

— *Proceedings* —

D&E 2016

10th International
Conference on
Design & Emotion

*Celebration &
Contemplation*

27 — 30 Sept 2016
Amsterdam

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— *Colofon* —

Proceedings of the Tenth International Conference on Design and Emotion –
Celebration & Contemplation

Amsterdam, September 27-30, 2016

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— Editorial —

These are the proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Design & Emotion, September 27-30, 2016, in Amsterdam, The Netherlands. The conference is a forum held every two years in which researchers, practitioners, and industry leaders meet to exchange knowledge and insights concerning the cross-disciplinary field of design and emotion.

Over the last 15 years, the field of Design & Emotion has increasingly become part of areas such as Design for Experience, User experience, Multi-sensory design, Design for well-being, Social design, and so forth, and has become widely spread and accepted. At several design research conferences, a separate Design & Emotion track has become commonplace. At the same time, in recent decades, other specific experience-related platforms have emerged. At the 10th conference in the Netherlands, we continued our efforts in bringing together design practitioners, researchers and industry. We again invited the D&E community to present their latest work and we welcomed cutting-edge designers and researchers as keynote speakers. But we also reflected on our raison d'être for the next 15 years. Which is why this edition, the theme of the conference was "Celebration & Contemplation"

These proceedings provide you with an overview of all the presented research papers, design cases, and workshops of the conference. The review of papers included in these proceedings was overseen by a program committee consisting of academics from five organizing institutions: Design & Emotion Society, Delft University of Technology, University of Twente, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences, and Waag Society.

The call for papers attracted 217 submissions from researchers of domains such as design, social sciences, arts, computer science, HCI, psychology, health sciences, marketing and business. After a double-blind review process, in which each submission was reviewed by at least two of 90 expert reviewers from 22 countries, 107 submissions were accepted (49%). These submissions were included in a rich program of oral presentations, poster presentations, and special session to be held by 300 delegates from 27 countries, accompanied by four keynote speakers and eight thought-leaders.

Following the conference the proceedings will be accessible through the Design & Emotion Society. A catalogue record of the digital proceedings and the book of abstracts is also be available through Elsevier Scopus.

We thank the authors for choosing to disseminate their research at this conference. We would also like to thank the reviewers who have been paramount in assuring the high quality of papers accepted for publication. In addition, we would like to thank the copyeditors, designers, and all the other people who have been instrumental in assuring the high quality of papers published in these proceedings.

We wish you an inspiring conference and hope that you will have lots of opportunity for celebration and contemplation.

The D&E 2016 Program Committee

— Themes & topics —

Design and emotion has been consistently the conference's overarching theme. With the conference's current motto "Celebration & Contemplation," we celebrate our tenth anniversary and take the opportunity to reflect on our raison d'être for the next 15 years. We invite original contributions aligned (but not limited) to the following eight conference topics:

1. Ambiguity

Designing rich experiences, irony, and uncomfortable interactions

2. Provocation

Design activism, future prototyping, and positive speculation

3. Well-being

Design for social behavior, ethics, happiness, and personal values

4. Beauty

Design aesthetics, materials, and the senses

5. Embodiment

Design ubiquity, internet, tangibility, and embedded computing

6. Poetry

Designing openness, drama, emotional durability, and storytelling

7. Empathy

Design for inclusion, participation, and co-design

8. Spirituality

Design for mindfulness, memories, trust experiences, and awe

— Conference Organization —

The 10th International Conference on Design & Emotion is organized by:

The Design & Emotion Society

The Design & Emotion society raises issues and facilitates dialogue among practitioners, researchers, and industry, in order to integrate salient themes of emotional experience into the design profession. The Design & Emotion society is established in 1999 as an international network of researchers, designers and companies sharing an interest in experience driven design. The network is used to exchange insights, research, tools and methods that support the involvement of emotional experience in product design. The daily board is based in The Netherlands.

Although the initiative originated from the discipline of product design and design research, through the years practitioners from other design disciplines such as interaction design and branding design, contributed and benefited from the network and activities.

the Design & Emotion society raises issues and facilitates dialogue among practitioners, researchers, and industry in order to integrate salient themes of emotional experience into the design profession

TU Delft, Faculty Industrial Design Engineering

Designing for our future. That is the core business of students and researchers at the faculty of Industrial Design Engineering of TU Delft. The faculty's mission is to contribute to the knowledge, skills, methods and professional attitudes in the field of integrated product development. This is achieved through education and research at an internationally recognized scientific level. Over 5.000 Industrial Design Engineers have graduated from the faculty since it was founded in 1969. IDE is still among the largest university design programmes in the world. Nowadays, the emphasis is on the design of durable products and services, taking into account the interests of users, industry, society and the environment. Perhaps design can even be used to stimulate users to change their behaviour, thus helping to solve (future) problems ranging from obesity to material scarcity.

University of Twente

The University of Twente is a young and enterprising university that prepares young people for the future. We accomplish this through innovative, attractive and future-focused education and through fulfilling a global function in technological and social research. Together, 3,300 researchers and professionals work on pioneering research, relevant innovations and inspiring education for more than 9,000 students. The University of Twente connects science and society through design at the Designlab, an open and creative environment for faculty and students from all fields. Top talents from engineering, natural science, social science and the humanities work together with companies and governments on societal design challenges of our times, inspired by novel scientific insights.

UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE.

Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences

Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS) provides best possible education and produce cutting-edge research in the areas of culture and society, trade, logistics, aviation, shipping, ICT, sport, healthcare, education and much more. AUAS have a total of 43,000 students and offer a total of 80 bachelor and master programmes. Practice-oriented research is an important component of the educational programmes offered by the seven faculties. The research always addresses a real-life world problem from the professional field, and is conducted in close collaboration with both academics and professionals working in the particular discipline. AUAS have 250 partner institutes across 50 different countries and contribute to various educational projects such as curriculum development, research projects, student/professor exchanges and work placements within an international working field. This ensures that the education provided by AUAS is truly internationally orientated.

Design Academy Eindhoven

Design Academy Eindhoven specialises in design. It offers a four-year Bachelor's course and a two-year Master's course. It has an impressive, international team of tutors at its disposal and the quality of the designers they educate is very high. The DNA of Design Academy Eindhoven can be described as conceptual, authentic, creative, flexible, free, passionate and curious. In the Academy's own view, its excellence lies in the fact that it trains designers to be aware of the social implications of their designs. This is why the Academy chooses a more horizontal and integral approach to design over the more traditional vertical structure within each design discipline. The link between this integrative approach on the one hand and autonomy as a principle on the other is characteristic of the Academy as an organisation and as an educational institution.

Waag Society

Waag Society - institute for art, science and technology - is a pioneer in the field of digital media. Over the past 22 years, the foundation has developed into an institution of international stature, a platform for artistic research and experimentation, and has become both a catalyst for events and a breeding ground for cultural and social innovation. Waag Society explores emerging technologies, and provides art and culture a central role in the design of new applications for novel advances in science and technology. It currently has six thematic research labs: the Open Design Lab, Future Heritage Lab, Future Internet Lab, Creative Learning Lab, Creative Care Lab, and the Open Wetlab.

— Conference organizers —

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— *Keynotes* —

The following cutting-edge Dutch designers gave a keynote speech during the opening and closing day of the conference.

— *Christien Meindertsma*

Christien Meindertsma is a Dutch conceptual designer. She explores the life of products and raw materials. For her first book, *Checked Baggage* (2004), Christien categorized 3267 items confiscated at security checkpoints in Schiphol Airport after 9/11. With her second book, *PIG 05049* (2007), documents an astounding array of products that different parts of an anonymous pig could support. With this book, Christien reveals lines that link raw materials with producers, products and consumers that have become so invisible in an increasingly globalized world. With her designs Christien aims to regain understanding of processes that have become so distant in industrialization. Her work has been exhibited in MOMA (New York), The V&A (London) and the Cooper Hewitt Design museum (New York).

— *Maarten Baas*

Maarten Baas is a Dutch designer, whose works lie on the boundaries between art and design and is known as rebellious, playful, intellectual, theatrical and artistic. It varies from conceptual designs and installations, to theater design and performances. His graduation work of a series of burned furniture called "Smoke", followed by his "Clay Furniture" collection, are both considered design classics. Baas has made successful solo presentations of his new works at the Salone del Mobile in Milan for many years, winning awards with his Real Time series and the exhibition called "Baas is in Town", inspired on circus and entertainment. Maarten's works are in major museum collections, such as the MoMa and Rijksmuseum and he works for exclusive brands such as Louis Vuitton and Swarovski.

— *Robert Winkel*

Architect Robert Winkel is driven by the desire to make marvellous things, heavy or light, big or small. With his team at MEI architects and planners he tirelessly works at designing projects that are the perfect fit, surprising us with unusual techniques, products, views and solutions.

To Winkel history is a generous source of inspiration leading to designs that are fresh and self-evident at once. It has resulted in a series of successful building transformations, like the Jobsveem and the Gouda Cheese Warehouse. He firmly believes that designing and producing belong together. This goes for smaller things like detailing and products, but also for bigger things like entire buildings. For Robert Winkel designing is a way of letting the heart speak and adding meaning to the world.

— *Pauline van Dongen*

Pauline van Dongen is a Dutch fashion designer and renowned expert in wearable technology. Her design studio is dedicated to collaborative, cross-disciplinary work that enables innovation and experimentation to take the form of a truly wearable and desirable product. As a creator interested in the notion of interactivity in fashion, Pauline researches the human body in relation to its surroundings. By integrating new materials and electronics in clothing, her goal is to create new types of interaction and behaviour that can contribute to the way we experience the world around us. Pauline's vision is based on the belief that technology can add new value and meaning to fashion and enhances embodied experience. She believes the future of fashion lies in its premise to be dynamic and responsive. To her, technology is not a mere tool, but rather one of aesthetics.

— Thought leaders —

Over the last 15 years, the Design & Emotion community has studied the broad field of design for experience. At our 10th conference, we wanted to celebrate our accomplishments in this field but we also wanted to contemplate, and ask ourselves what we should aim for in the next 15 years. Wouldn't it be interesting to explore new territories? Wouldn't it be wonderful to expand our horizon?

The broad Design & Emotion community has proven to be dedicated and committed, an ideal group for a relevant discussion like this. To that end, we hosted four 'thought leader sessions', to explore and discuss possible future directions for the Design & Emotion Society. In each session, two thought leaders, prominent researchers in areas related to design & emotion, paired up to share their perspective on one of four themes: 'Enhancing everyday life'; 'Design & Responsibility'; 'Technology for a better society' and 'A transformation to happiness'. The outcomes of the sessions were aggregated, and used as the basis for a new mission statement that was presented at the closing ceremony of the conference.

The following eight thought leaders presented and debated their vision on Design & Emotion:

Enhancing everyday life

Jodi Forlizzi

Jodi Forlizzi is a Professor of Human-Computer Interaction in the School of Computer Science at Carnegie Mellon University and a co-founder of Pratter.us, a healthcare startup. Her research ranges from understanding the limits of human attention to understanding how products and services evoke social behavior. She designs and researches systems ranging from peripheral displays to social and assistive robots. Her current research interests include designing educational games that are engaging

and effective, designing services that adapt to people's needs, and designing for healthcare. Jodi is a member of the ACM CHI Academy and has been honored by the Walter Reed Army Medical Center for excellence in HRI design research. Jodi has consulted with Disney and General Motors to create innovative product-service systems.

Adrian Cheok

Adrian David Cheok is Director of the Imagineering Institute, Malaysia as well as Professor of Pervasive Computing at City University London. He is Founder and Director of the Mixed Reality Lab, Singapore. Adrian has been working on research covering mixed reality, human-computer interfaces, wearable computers, pervasive and ubiquitous computing. The research output has included numerous high quality academic journal papers, research awards, keynote speeches and hundreds of international press media articles. Adrian is also Editor in Chief of the academic journals: ACM Computers in Entertainment, Transactions on Edutainment (Springer), and Lovotics: Academic Studies of Love and Friendship with Robots.

Sustainable stories

Jonathan Chapman

Jonathan Chapman is Professor of Sustainable Design, Director of Design Research Initiatives and Chair of the University of Brighton's Professorial Board (Arts & Humanities). Best known for his concept of 'emotionally durable design', his research into the emotional dimensions of product longevity has advanced design and business thinking in a range of settings, from Sony, Puma, Philips and The Body Shop to the House of Lords and the UN.

Nynke Tromp

Nynke Tromp works as an assistant professor Social Design & Behaviour Change at the department of Industrial Design, Delft University of Technology. After her PhD and working as a social designer in practice at Reframing Studio, she now continues her study to the value of design in counteracting social problems. Tromp is intrigued by the fact that products change behaviour, often without people being aware of it, and often unintentionally. Tromp worked on social challenges like organ donation, political engagement of citizens, and recovery from psychosis. In 2013, she won the Rotterdam Design Prize for temstem, a smartphone application to help people cope with hearing voices (developed at Reframing Studio).

Technology for a better society

Sebastian Deterding

Sebastian Deterding is a designer-researcher working on playful, motivational, and eudaimonic design. His work asks how to re-design our socio-technical systems to enable a good life for all. In secular societies with plural visions of the good life, how can we empower people to deliberate what the good life means to them, and to transform their life world accordingly? Sebastian is a senior research fellow at the Digital Creativity Labs at the University of York. Founder of the design agency coding conduct and associate of Hubbub, he has created engaging experiences touching millions of users for clients including the BBC, BMW, Deutsche Telekom, and KLM. He is founder of the Gamification Research Network, and co-editor of *The Gameful World* (MIT Press 2015). He lives online at codingconduct.cc.

Vanessa Evers

Vanessa Evers is a full professor of Computer Science at the University of Twente's Human Media Interaction group. Her research interests focus on interaction with intelligent and autonomous systems such as robots as well as cultural aspects of Human Computer Interaction. She has published over 80 peer reviewed publications, many of which in high quality journals and conferences in human computer interaction and human robot interaction. Vanessa is an editor for the International Journal of Social Robotics and Associate Editor of the Human Robot Interaction Journal.

A transformation to happiness

Andrea Gaggioli

Dr. Andrea Gaggioli is Professor of Psychology in the Faculty of Psychology at Catholic University of Sacred Heart in Milan, Italy. His main focus is on Positive Technology, a field at the intersection of interaction design, neuroscience and positive psychology, which investigates how interactive technologies can be used to empower cognition and foster mental wellbeing. Andrea has authored many peer-reviewed papers concerning the applications of emerging technologies in mental health and neurorehabilitation. For his scientific work, he received several

international acknowledgements, including the Prize of the European Academy of Rehabilitation Medicine.

Marc Hassenzahl

Dr. Marc Hassenzahl is professor for Experience Design at the Folkwang University of the Arts in Essen, Germany. He combines his training in psychology with a love for interaction design. With his group of designers and psychologists, he explores the theory and practice of designing pleasurable and transforming interactive technologies. Marc is author of "Experience Design. Technology for all the right reasons" and many peer-reviewed papers at the seams of psychology, design research and interaction/industrial design.

— Pre-conference workshops —

The day prior to the conference, we offered four workshops that were organized by our partner organizations. About 80 delegates participated to learn about tools and methods for specific design (research) challenges.

Design for our future self: Exploring new ways to give 'voice' to the users' needs within the context of dementia

Organized by Waag Society: Sabine Wildevuur, Hester van Zuthem & Janine Huizenga; and University of Applied Sciences Amsterdam: Nazli Cila, in collaboration with VUcm: Fleur Thomese.

The purpose of the workshop is to learn from each other by active discussion and making, share and exchange insights on person-centered design methodologies and solutions, particularly people with dementia and their careers.

The current focus on caring and dementia research is often focused on finding a cure, instead of finding ways to live a good (and dignified) life when dealing with dementia. However, there is a growing interest in more person-centered initiatives that empower people in terms of living more autonomously, such as dementia friendly neighborhoods. In line with Huber's definition of positive health, this workshop takes a positive, person-centered design approach to caring solutions. Huber et al. (2011): "Health is the ability to adapt and self-manage in the face of social, physical, and emotional challenges."

Design Research Lexicon. Exploring The Vocabulary

Organized by Design Academy Eindhoven: Bas Raijmakers, David Hamers, Danielle Arets, Liesbeth Fit, Irene Fortuyn & Joost Grootens.

The last two years the Knowledge Circle of the two Readerships at Design Academy Eindhoven has worked on a lexicon of design research in which crucial concepts and terms are being defined by text as well as with images of DAE student projects that embody these research terms. At DAE design research happens in all departments and readerships but do we really share the same language when we talk about mapping, or empathy?

With the Design Research lexicon, we have tried to capture our design research practice in a shared vocabulary that allows us to describe and understand what we have in common. The lexicon contains a variety of concepts that play an important role in Design Research practice. Of course this list cannot be exhaustive. Moreover, the lexicon is never finished, just like the design research practice at DAE keeps moving, the lexicon does too. The lexicon is an invitation to engage in a dialogue with our colleagues, fellow design researchers as well as with design students.

Home is where the heart is. Experience a multidisciplinary approach to give high-tech home care a human touch

Organized by University of Twente: Geke Ludden, Peter-Paul Verbeek & Mascha van der Voort.

Meaningful innovations can only emerge from a symbiosis of high-tech science and a thorough understanding of the relations between technology, society, and people. In this workshop, we will offer participants the unique experience of truly multidisciplinary work within a case that is relevant from a science and a society perspective: The recent paradigm shift in the organization of healthcare that places (ICT supported) care technology in the homes and lives of people calls for a deeper analysis of the impact of this development. Important questions arise as to how this development will affect the (perceived) quality of care and people's feeling of independence. Further, questions have to be asked about what technology we need and how care technology has to be developed in such a way that people will not feel threatened by allowing the technology into their home, but rather, are confident to welcome it into their lives. These questions can only be solved by following a multidisciplinary approach. Issues that arise are for example that people have to be able to use and understand the medical technology, smart, connected sensors and devices are needed to take physiological measurements non-intrusively and these measurements have to be communicated to end-users and caregivers.

During the workshop, we will work on the case as specified by following the main steps in the Science2Design4Society approach of the Utwente DesignLab. Peter-Paul Verbeek, professor of philosophy of technology and Mascha van der Voort, professor of Human Centred Design will introduce the Science2Design4Society approach.

Positive Design. Designing the road of happiness.

Organized by Delft University of Technology: Anna Pohlmeier & Pieter Desmet.

"If you want to increase your happiness, don't buy new products, change your behaviour." Positive psychologists sometimes advise that not too much ought to be expected from the contributions to subjective well-being made by consumer products (Nicolao, Irwin, & Goodman, 2009). The 'Positive Design' workshop challenges this view by proposing that design can increase happiness. The central question addressed is: How can design contribute to human flourishing? Positive Design is an umbrella term for all forms of design, design research and design intention in which explicit attention is paid to the effects of design on the subjective well-being of individuals and communities (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013; Pohlmeier & Desmet, 2014). In their workshop, Anna and Pieter will introduce their view on Positive Design and present examples of how design can help people in finding balance between pleasure, purpose in life, and virtuous behaviour. They will introduce some of the key research questions in the domain of Positive Design and detail a Positive Design Framework in-depth. In addition to providing relevant background knowledge, a number of hands-on exercises will be conducted to familiarize participants with essential concepts and design methods. The aim of the workshop is to inform, engage, and inspire; offering a balance between theory & research on the one hand, and experiences & design examples on the other.

— Overview of contributions —

Authors submitted contributions in four categories: Full papers, Short papers, Pictorials, and Special sessions.

Full Papers

Full papers are a maximum of 5000 words and present a widely applicable and long-lasting contribution to the body of knowledge of the discipline. Full papers were presented orally at the conference.

Tellme: From user to developer in one click Derya Ozcelik-Buskermolen, Abbie Vanhoutte, Andrea Meessen, Ruben Hekkens, Nanne Krikke, Merijn Neeleman	28-36
Laugh: Designing to enhance positive emotion for people living with dementia Cathy Treadaway, Gail Kenning, David Prytherch, Jac Fennell	37-44
The effects of enlarged words in text messages: Look clearer, but less premium Do-hyeong Kim, Suhong Ju, Eunjin Kim, Hyeon-Jeong Suk	45-51
Perfect Days. A benevolent calendar to take back your time Marc Hassenzahl, Dan Buzzo, Robin Neuhaus	52-58
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— *Full Papers* —

Tellme: From user to developer in one click

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Abstract Tellme is a new user research tool that connects qualitative user feedback to quantitative product data in business-to-business environments. The concept consists of a mobile application and a dashboard. Through the mobile application qualitative user feedback is obtained during prolonged use of products. This feedback is connected to the quantitative product data of these products (data logging) and shown real-time to the design and development team via a monitoring dashboard. As such the development team can not only empathize with the users they are designing for, but also immediately address the obtained feedback during development. This increases the probability that the end-product will fulfill the end-user's needs and expectations.

In this paper we will first discuss our motivation to develop Tellme. We will give an overview of existing tools and methods related to Tellme. We will introduce Tellme and report a case where Tellme was used. We will conclude the paper by discussing its use in new product development processes.

Keywords *Empathy, Customer intimacy, Product validation, B2B user research, User research tools*

Introduction

At Océ – a Canon Company, we are developing professional print systems that are used in commercial contexts by professional users. We acknowledge that for making the right product, it is crucial to obtain knowledge about users, their environments and their experiences with our products. User-centered design is the core of our new product development processes. We use established methods and tools like contextual inquiry, personas, usability testing and product validations at customer sites before our products are released. However, new product development processes are changing. The pressure on time-to-market is increasing, leading to a tension between research and development. To pursue our user-centered approach we need to have means to easily get feedback from users and to communicate this feedback quickly and effectively to the development teams.

Developers often base their assessment of product success mainly on statistics (product data): if the numbers are right, the product must be working correctly. Being able to monitor critical product parameters remotely is an innovation that helps developers to improve products in a quick way, yet it does not help them to understand the everyday reality of users. For this purpose we have developed Tellme.

Through Tellme the reality of a product's parameters captured in quantitative product data is combined with rich insights provided by the product's users. By aggregating and communicating this information directly to the development team, a dialogue between user, product data and developer is created. The developers not only get a comprehensive overview of

the product's performance, but they are also enabled to understand and empathize with the users. Based on these insights, necessary improvements can already be implemented during product development. This saves time and resources and increases the likelihood that the end-product will fulfill the users' needs and expectations.

In this paper we will first discuss our motivation to develop Tellme. We will give an overview of existing tools and methods related to Tellme. We will introduce Tellme and report a case where Tellme was used. We will conclude the paper by discussing its value in new product development processes.

Challenges of doing user research in B2B contexts

Océ develops professional print systems for business-to-business (B2B) environments. Following a user-centered design process in a B2B context brings along some challenges.

In a B2B context, end-users are trained professionals. They have specific expertise and advanced tasks and responsibilities. It is therefore more difficult for designers to understand and empathize with such professionals, because their experience, expertise and mind-set are different. Designers need to be informed very well about the users they are designing for, in order to know their activities and understand their needs.

In a B2C context the user who provides the budget, considers options, makes the decision to purchase, purchases and uses the product, is one single person. However, in a B2B context different stakeholders are

involved in each stage. Even though the end-user experience is still in the focus, the needs and expectations of all these stakeholders should be considered during a new product development process (Nielsen, 2006).

Reaching the end-users, getting their commitment and motivating them to participate in user research can also be cumbersome. Different channels such as business units, sales organizations, service organizations and the users' management, are inquired to establish contact with end-users. This long path de-motivates design professionals and makes them incline to get user feedback indirectly from user representatives and/or experts (Özçelik et al., 2011). This however involves the risk of filtered and biased information.

Since it concerns their professional activities, getting end-users' motivation to participate in user research is also challenging. On the one hand, they appreciate being asked for their opinion; on the other hand, the research is of secondary importance as their daily work will always have priority.

Another challenge lies in the products' nature. Products developed for B2B contexts are professional products. They have complex specifications, are integrated in a specific workflow and are used with other products and software systems. These products are used by different end-users who have different roles in a workflow. This complexity strengthens the importance of user-centered design and usability in a B2B context (Nielsen, 2006); however, it brings also the strong need to have a thorough understanding of the professional contexts and related workflows.

Nowadays data logging is widely used by companies, especially in B2B contexts, to get insights in the usage patterns of products. Intelligence built in these products sends data about pre-determined areas of interest; such as volume of production, number of errors and consumption of resources. Even though data logging provides continuous flows of large amounts of data, it has some limitations. Firstly, it cannot capture unexpected insights because the data which would be extracted from the device should be coded beforehand. Secondly, it provides insights only regarding quantifiable measures and can only support product development regarding those aspects. For example, it is difficult to capture experiential and affective aspects of user experience through data logging.

All these challenges, together with the desire to bring breakthrough products to the market with decreasing lead times, require us to update our portfolio of user research tools and methods. The development of Tellme is motivated by these concerns.

The tools and methods used in user-centered design processes at Océ

In order to understand our professional users and their latent needs, we use several methods. Amongst those are contextual inquiries, cultural probes and beta testing.

With the contextual inquiry method (Holtzblatt and Jones, 1993), we interview end-users and observe their ongoing work in their natural work contexts. During a full day, an employee from Research and Development (R&D) observes professional users at work in a print production environment. The contextual inquiry method allows us to examine and describe actual workflows of customers in detail. Information is gathered on how work is done with the tools at hand. The generated data are very rich and effectively communicating insights to the development team is a challenge.

Cultural probes (Gaver, Dunne and Pacenti, 1999) are another tool to gather information about end-users. Users are given booklets containing a small amount of creative assignments that encourage them to reflect on their experience with a certain product. However, we also experience some limitations which are also mentioned by Lucero and Mattelmaki (2007). It takes time of the participants during their working hours. Next to that, there is neither dialogue nor interaction with the participants during the period they fill in the booklets. We never know whether they are using the probes as instructed until we get the results. Moreover, there might be urgent feedback, but this can only be addressed after the research period.

To validate whether our products fit within the complex environments of our customers, we conduct beta tests. During a beta test a product is exposed to the real world and tested by target users. In the later phases of a development process, a small number of prototypes are placed at selected customer sites. The customer commits to using the product for a couple of weeks and giving feedback on the strong points and what should be improved before the final product is introduced to the market. At several moments during this process, we conduct interviews with users. Based on this, several improvements can be implemented in the final product. Next to that, features for the second iteration and ideas for future products are inspired by the feedback of users. In this respect, ensuring a continuous feedback flow from users to the development team is really crucial. In practice however, this is often challenging. Not everybody from the development team can visit the customer sites, so it is hard to transfer the real customer knowledge to the whole development team. As time and resources for improvements are limited, it is crucial to highlight the most important issues and to convince the developers to take initiatives to improve them.

Tellme tackles the limitations of the current user-centered design research tools used by Océ. It enables our users to communicate their feedback real-time to the development team, in an interactive and effective way. As such we create a comprehensive dialogue with users at customer environments.

Tellme: creating a dialogue between users, product data and developers

Tellme consists of a mobile application that is used by end-users, and a monitoring dashboard for the development team. A moderator facilitates the connection between both.

Figure 1. Tellme mobile application.

The mobile application

The Tellme App is a qualitative research tool that runs on a smart phone. Via the application, end-users at customer sites can directly provide feedback about their experiences with our products. Depending on the time they have, the message they want to send, or their personal preferences to communicate, they can choose different means to communicate their feedback: responding to built-in surveys, sharing ad-hoc feedback, sending pictures and expressing emotions with smiley's (Figure 1). The development team can respond to this feedback by asking further questions and giving tips to optimize the user's experience.

The survey - based on the method of cultural probes - consists of questions and assignments prepared by a user researcher in the development team. During the study, every day one question becomes available for the participants. When the question is available, its color turns green on the main screen. Answered questions are marked blue and pending questions are marked orange. As such, the progress of the participant is made visible.

Participants can also directly share their ad-hoc feedback with the development team at any time during the research. They can attach pictures and movies to better explain their point. Next to that, participants can also express their emotions by means of smileys, with the option to explain their choice for a certain emotion. Finally, participants can receive ad-hoc questions from the development team. They can answer the question by means of a text message, when desired, accompanied by pictures or videos. Participants also receive tips from the development team which can help them to use the product in a more easy and efficient way. This two-way communication and personal attention motivates the participants to provide continuous and rich feedback. The feedback that is generated via the application provides deep and rich insights in the experiences of the users of our products.

The monitoring dashboard

The Tellme dashboard (Figure 2) shows an overview of the user feedback gathered through the mobile application, combined with printer data that are collected via logging. Logging is a technique that is used in combination with an electronic device, which automatically collects data by a system or a server (Schmid, 2012). This combination of both quantitative and qualitative information gives a unique insight into the product's performance and at the same time how users are experiencing the product.

In the dashboard, the emotional expressions indicating the mood of the participants are mapped on the quantitative data logged from the product. Next to that, a time-line with messages and images is presented. Furthermore, the dashboard shows the survey results, visualized in word clouds. Positive and negative remarks are clustered per topic. The participants' replies to the ad-hoc questions are also presented, together with their feedback and the pictures shared via the application. The home screen shows the general overview, while detailed information can be reached through navigating to sub-screens (Figure 3).

To make sure the development team can directly see the feedback coming from the customer sites, the dashboard is presented on a big touch screen placed in the project room (Figure 4) and can also be reached via an internal webpage. Rich infographics give the development team a real-time overview of the users' actual experience (qualitative information) combined with the product's performance (quantitative data). These direct insights allow the development team to empathize with the users, to comprehend their feedback and to understand the context of the product they are developing. This inspires and supports the development team to make the right choices, based on real use cases and user feedback.

Figure 2. Tellme monitoring dashboard.

Figure 3. Ub-screen of the dashboard showing the feedback of users on different aspects.

Figure 4. Development team looking at the Tellme dashboard in the project room.

The moderator

The two-way flow of information between the mobile application and the dashboard is managed by a moderator. This person is an independent user researcher, who works for the development team and who leads the user study. The workflow is shown in Figure 5.

Accordingly,

- Moderator defines questions and sends them to the user via the app
- The user answers the questions (at his/her convenience)
- This feedback is sent to the moderator via the app
- The moderator analyses and clusters the information, decides what and how to present it (e.g. word cloud, clusters, timeline) and forwards this info on the dashboard
- Data logging from the printer is sent directly to the dashboard
- The development team looks at the dashboard, interprets it and this inspires extra questions and/or advice for the users
- These ad hoc questions and/or advice are sent to the user via the app through the moderator

Relation to existing tools and methods

Tellme is strongly related to cultural probes. Since they have been introduced, cultural probes are widely embraced by the design research community. However, they have also evolved resulting from the adaptation of the tool to the needs of the research. Literature research reveals divergent uses of cultural probes and related tools derived from them (Boehner et al., 2007). Especially internet and advancement of smart technologies leads to a new generation of, more technology based, probes; such as technology probes (Hutchinson et al., 2003) and mobile probes (Hulkko et al., 2004). These probes are mainly used as means to collect information from users through the use of available technology. Today smart phones provide a wide range of means to collect information through the use of technology embedded in them; such as cameras, GPS and sensors. While developing the Tellme App, we were inspired by probes as a method of data collection and we used smart phones as means to achieve that. However, the Tellme concept is more than just the Tellme App. The data collected through the application is coupled to the Tellme dashboard.

Figure 5. The workflow of Tellme.

Case study

The study

Tellme was used to validate a new print system of Océ. A first version of this product was installed at a selected number of customer sites. The goal of this study was twofold: to get user feedback on the product and to get user feedback on the Tellme concept. In this paper we will only share the feedback on Tellme.

The study was conducted in the early phases of the development of Tellme. A prototype of the Tellme App and Dashboard were used in the study (Figure 6).

The study was conducted with 8 participants at 3 print production sites. One site was an internal Océ R&D environment, where hired print operators operated the product for the purpose of testing. The other two were customer sites where the new printer was recently installed. All participants were professional operators working in shifts. They used the Tellme App during their work. The development team of Océ also participated in the study, as users of the Tellme Dashboard. A usability designer from the Océ Design department was the moderator in this study.

The Tellme App was installed on phones owned by Océ and provided to the participants. Two phones were used per customer site. The study in the different sites was carried out in sequence and lasted one week per site. Users were informed about the research up front. They were explained that the information and the multimedia materials they sent would be visible to the development team, but for internal use only.

The Tellme Dashboard was placed in the project room of the development team. Part of the feedback coming from users was shown directly on the dashboard; such as the smileys and the word clouds. Other feedback, such as opinions and experiences, was first analyzed by the moderator and then posted on the dashboard in an organized way.

Figure 6. Prototype of Tellme mobile application (left) and dashboard (right).

Findings and discussion

We collected feedback on Tellme from the operators (users of the app), as well as the development team (users of the dashboard). The feedback from all 8 operators was collected by means of an interview by telephone during the test period (10 minutes) and a face-to-face interview at the end of the test (30 minutes). The topics included a.o. their general experiences, pro and contra, usability, suggestions for improvements. Some operators also sent feedback by means of the app. Feedback of 8 engineers from the development team was collected during and after the study by short, individual, face-to-face interviews. Below, the findings based on this feedback are described.

Users

From this study we learned that operators appreciated the Tellme App and found it easy to use. Giving feedback by means of the app was perceived as ‘fun’ and – contrary to our expectations - not too time-consuming. Users said that the use of smileys made it easier for them to quickly express their mood. Moreover, they added some playfulness. Being able to send pictures was also appreciated. Pictures made the feedback more concrete and prompted less need for long explanations, which saves time. One participant said that he preferred an app to an analogue diary (known as cultural probes). He said that it is easier to work with and more direct. Moreover, diaries can get lost easily in a work environment. The users liked the fact that there is a dialogue with the development team via a smart phone. They valued that their opinions are asked and taken seriously. Being part of such a research gave them the feeling that their feedback contributes to the improvement of the products they are working with.

Participants also had some suggestions for improving the app. The app should give better feedback when users answer a question or send a message. They would like to have confirmation that their message has reached the development team. Typing a lot of text on a smart phone was considered somewhat cumbersome. Even though the smiley’s and the inclusion of pictures

helped, they would also appreciate a speech-to-text tool to create text input.

As discussed earlier, keeping users motivated during a user research in a B2B context is a crucial aspect to get good results. Previous experiences also revealed that working with cultural probes in a business environment can be perceived as cumbersome for the participants. It can be regarded as an obligation which would diminish participants’ motivation to contribute to the research (Lucero and Mattelmaki, 2007; Lucero et al., 2004). However, we did not encounter that issue in our study. Participants were enthusiastic and their enthusiasm did not diminish during the study. We think that there were two reasons for it. Firstly, we have a long-term business relationship with the customers who participated in the study. Thus they were aware of the fact that the feedback they provide is taken seriously. It will improve the product and at the end they will benefit from it. Secondly, the feedback showed that use of smart phones made the process of providing feedback easier, more playful and more interesting for the participants. Furthermore, the app made the whole process more interactive. They got responses to their feedback, some extra questions and they were sent some tips helping them with their work. This interaction also prevented the motivation to drop.

Development team

Developers and designers working in the project were enthusiastic about the Tellme dashboard. They appreciated having direct access to the real-time feedback of users linked with product data. They liked seeing the general information in one view, but also expressed the need to be able to look into more details by clicking on specific items. They indicated that they would like to easily access the user researcher who is leading the study (the moderator) to be able to ask further questions to the users.

The development team was very interested in the real user quotes and pictures. They said that the user quotes reveal the motivation behind the feedback and also the nuances. User quotes and pictures linked to

product data made the information more vivid and trustworthy. The quotes helped the designers to create empathy with the users and get a better understanding of their experience with the product.

The use of visualizations at the home page was appreciated, because they helped the development team to get a quick overview and prioritize the user feedback. Especially the combination of quantitative and qualitative information triggered reactions and led to discussions in the team. For example: once the data showed that the printer was performing very well (no errors, high uptime), but one operator expressed a sad smiley. This unexpected combination triggered the development team to dive deeper into the user experience to find out what was causing the problem and the motivation behind the feedback. We think that Tellme was appreciated and embraced by the development team because it provided direct, clear user feedback linked to product data, and at the same time it gave them the opportunity to ask more details if they had further questions.

Our study showed that direct contact between development team and the users helped the team to understand the users and their feedback better. Normally, the development team does not have much contact with the users. Most of the user information available for the development team comes through service and sales departments because they have more direct contact with customers. However, this information is usually filtered as people make their own interpretations of what they see and hear.

Moderator

The moderator has an important role in analyzing, clustering and responding to the feedback. During this study, the moderator spent 2 hours per day on this. When the group of users becomes bigger, this will be more time consuming. We think that in the future, part of the moderation can be automated through the use of intelligent tags. As such the tool becomes less resource intensive. We believe however, that the 'human factor' of the moderator is essential in facilitating the dialogue between the users and the development team. They can guide discussions within the development team based on the feedback in the Tellme Dashboard. Next to that, users should not get the feeling they are receiving computer generated responses.

The challenge of the moderator role lies in the interpretation of the user feedback. It is important that this is done in an unbiased way, and that the development team trusts the objective and independent interpretation of this usability professional.

Improvements Tellme

Based on the feedback obtained from the users and development team, we improved the design of both the mobile application and the dashboard. Improvements were aimed making the visual design more readable, understandable and attractive (Figure 7) and therefore increasing the usability.

In the future, we foresee more improvements of the tool, for example making more use of technologies available within smart phones such as using GPS to track the movement of users in their work environment and using speech-to-text to facilitate text input.

Recommendations

Even though Tellme was developed within the context of Océ, we believe this tool has the opportunity to provide value to other companies working in a B2B context. Here we would like to share some recommendations regarding the adaptation and the use of the tool.

Firstly, both the app and the dashboard require some adaptation before it can be used in another context. To a big extent, the app can be used as is. The concepts used to collect the users' feedback, questions and moods can stay intact as the content of those is provided by the user. However, the survey questions and assignments should be reconsidered depending on the aim of the research and the type of product. Using the same concepts for similar kinds of assignments and updating just the content would make the adaptation easier. The same is also valid for the dashboard. Several concepts were used to represent information, such as the word cloud, the infographics and the quotes. Even if the content varies, the same concepts can still be used. Adapting the data logging system would be the most difficult part. For that the product itself should be designed as such at it sends usage data to the dashboard.

Conducting qualitative research with a large number of participants and analyzing all the information they provide is costly and labor intensive. Provided that the user research is done with a well defined target user group and the aim of the research is to get user feedback on the product under development (and not to assess hypotheses regarding variations within the target group), we think that using Tellme within a user research with 8 participants will lead to useful results. Eight participants can be distributed over different customer sites.

We also have some recommendations regarding how the research is conducted. As in every user research, it is important that the research goals are clearly communicated to the users and they are informed upfront about what is expected from them. If possible, we recommend having face to face contact with participants at the beginning of the research. It helps the researcher to get to know the users and the customer site and to build up rapport with the participants. It also gives room to the participants to ask questions about the tool and the research. It is also important to manage the expectations of the participants. It should be communicated upfront that Tellme is not a "WhatsApp" like application, but has a response-time similar to e-mail communication. Moreover, participants should be informed that the information and pictures they send via the app will be treated confidentially, for internal use only.

Figure 7. Improvements on the design (left-top: first prototype of the app, left-bottom: first prototype of the dashboard, right-top: second version of the app, right bottom: second version of the dashboard).

Conclusions

This paper has been concerned with conducting user research to inform the product development team in a B2B context. We have presented a new tool, Tellme, which has been developed by Océ to obtain user feedback on products that are under development. Through Tellme the development team can receive direct feedback from users, combined with real-time data from the print system they are using. This combination of both qualitative and quantitative information is a strong asset for the development team. It enables them to understand and empathize with the users they are designing for of the developed system. They can use the feedback in their discussions and during the process of decision making. Traditional methods for customer research often take much time to execute, analyze the results and share with the development team. Tellme however, provides real-time feedback in an effective way. As such the team can have access to the user feedback much earlier during development process which leads to well-motivated decisions and saves time and money for repair work.

Tellme also adds value for the customer. With Tellme the customers feel that their opinions are taken seriously and they are acknowledged as stakeholders in new product development. They appreciate the interactive dialogue and the response to their feedback. They feel they are contributing to the improvement of the products they will be using. This strengthening of relations between Océ and its customers is key in being successful in a B2B market

where products are investment goods and relations between producer and customer are long-term by definition.

To summarize, Tellme creates a dialogue between user, product data and developers. It helps us to understand what our customers really want. We can quickly react on their needs and that enables us to create the right products for them. Furthermore, the direct contact with our customers during product development and asking for their feedback strengthens customer relations. The combination of both outcomes enhances our business.

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LAUGH: Designing to enhance positive emotion for people living with dementia

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Abstract Dementia comprises a number of degenerative neurological diseases. It is a complex condition and each person's experience and symptoms are different. There is a growing awareness of the need for well-designed products and services to assist with dementia care and to enhance wellbeing. This paper presents research investigating the design of playful objects for people with late stage dementia. The investigation described is a preliminary stage in the LAUGH (Ludic Artefacts Using Gesture and Haptics) project; an AHRC funded international, interdisciplinary design research project. People living with dementia, informal and professional carers, health professionals, art therapists, charity representatives, arts practitioners and designers are informing the research through a series of expert group participatory workshops and case study interviews. Observation, discussion, video, photography and reflective journals have been used to analyse and document the investigation. Findings presented in this paper focus on the importance of emotional memory and emotional expression in the care of people with late stage dementia; the value of sensory triggers and props to stimulate emotional remembering; and the importance of designing to promote high quality social connections between people. These findings will inform the future design prototyping and development stage of the LAUGH research.

Keywords Design, Dementia, Emotion, Play, Memory

Context

The number of people living with dementia worldwide is predicted to rise significantly over the next twenty years (Prince et al., 2015; WHO, 2012). The anticipated consequence of this on many societies around the world will be a steep increase in the requirement for provision of long-term specialist residential dementia care, in particular for people in the later stages of the disease, as well as respite care support for their families (RSA, 2012). Dementia detrimentally impacts memory, perception, communication and in particular, it disrupts associative thought processes. The condition comprises a number of degenerative neurological diseases, the most common of which are Alzheimer's disease and vascular dementia. Dementia is a complex condition; each person's experience and symptoms are different and the progression of the disease is individual and unique (Hughes, 2014).

There is a growing awareness of the lack of well-designed products and services to assist with dementia care and to enhance wellbeing (Design Council, 2012). The complexity of the disease is a challenge for designers. Design research is needed to develop new understandings, approaches, services and products to support both the practicalities of day-to-day care and also the emotional wellbeing of those living with the disease.

This paper describes international design research currently underway in the UK and Australia. The work focuses specifically on developing designs for playful

objects that stimulate positive emotion and increase subjective wellbeing for people with late stage dementia living in residential care. The LAUGH project is a three-year international research project funded by the UK Arts and Humanities Research Council and supported by the care industry and leading charities in the field including Alzheimer's Society and Age UK. Preliminary findings emerging from the first phase of participatory workshops and case study interviews are presented in this paper.

Understanding positive emotion

Many people in long-term dementia care suffer from depression (Chenoweth et al., 2009). Anti depressant and anti psychotic medication is widely used in residential care to treat both depression and the perceived associated challenging behaviours. There is however, growing research from academia, medical and care professionals to support non-pharmacological psychosocial approaches to care; these include music and singing, visual art appreciation and creative playful activities (Brooker & Duce, 2000; Zeisel, 2011). These approaches stimulate positive emotion *in the moment* and there is growing evidence that these activities provide sustained benefits to subjective wellbeing over the longer term (Killick, 2013). There are significant economic advantages to reducing the need for medication; for people living with dementia and their families there is also the potential for a richer experience of *living well*, as opposed to *existing* with the disease (Killick, 2013). These new approaches will challenge conventional

care patterns (Zeisel, 2011).

Research indicates that there is currently very little for people with late stage dementia to do, resulting in feelings of boredom and isolation (Chenoweth et al., 2014). As the disease progresses, verbal communication becomes increasingly difficult and moments of connection with other people, which are vital for sustaining positive emotion, are reduced. Studies in psychology by (Fredrickson, 2014) have shown that *positivity resonance* or moments of *high quality connection* between people, benefits not only mental health but also individual physiology and wellbeing. By broadening empathic moments of connection between people it is possible to lower heart rates, reduce stress, boost the immune system, lower blood pressure as well as developing a more positive outlook on life (Fredrickson, 2014).

Understanding how positive emotions manifest, what they 'look like' and how they 'feel' is vital for the development of new designs that are able to increase personal emotional wellbeing and support moments of high quality connections between people living with dementia, their family and carers. There is also a need to understand how positive emotion relates to memory, reminiscence and perception of experience, since memory impairment plays a significant role in how the diseases presents. Emotional memory is however, subjective, located with the individual, and difficult to elucidate (LeDoux, 1998).

The following sections describe a study that was designed to elicit moments of emotional remembering in the study participants, and make evident the processes involved in the reconstruction of emotional memory (Dourish, 2006). The study described is only a small part of the wider LAUGH design research project. Its purpose was to illuminate the common human experience of emotional memory and use this knowledge to inform the design of objects to be used in dementia care. The study therefore, involved participants who were experts involved in dementia care and who were able to identify and articulate how their own experiences of emotional memory might *correlate* or *differ* from people living with late stage dementia¹.

Methodology

The LAUGH design research uses Positive Design approaches in the development of playful objects for people with late stage dementia (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). Building on methods used by international researchers working in the field of design for dementia, the research described in this paper is qualitative, inclusive and participatory (Bhömer, Tomico, Kleinsmann, Kuusk, & Wensveen, 2012; Branekaert, Snaphaan, & Ouden, 2014). The project is informed by the 'distributed expertise' of people living with dementia, care professionals and informal carers, as well as practice-based creative design in which physical objects are constructed as data for interrogation. These objects comprise paper prototypes, storyboards and models as well as photographs, video and reflective journals.

Prior to the study described in this paper, two inclusive participatory workshops and four interviews were held over a period of six months to gather data to inform the LAUGH design research process. Participants attending these events formed an expert group including health professionals, carers, care managers, occupational therapists, charity representatives, people with dementia and academic researchers. Three case study interviews with healthcare professionals and a focus group with an Alzheimer's Service Users Panel comprising three people with dementia have also informed this study.

The workshops were held in the National Centre for Product Design Research, Cardiff Met University, in the User Centred Design Laboratory. The UCD lab is fully equipped with a video recording system capable of capturing four areas in the room. Data is fed to an adjacent room housing an editing suit running Noldus Observer XT® software, used to tag and analyse the video data. Still photography and audio recordings were also made to capture and document each event. Both workshops involved participants engaging in creative activities and the resulting artefacts were analysed to inform the research. Workshop 1 focused on the theme of hand-use and play. Participants were encouraged to reflect on practical handcraft activities such as bread making and making simple toys, as well as playing games involving the hands; the findings arising from it are discussed in detail in (Treadaway, Prytherch, Kenning, & Fennell, 2016). The second workshop specifically addressed questions concerning emotional memory and positive emotion and is described in detail in the following section of this paper.

Expert Group: Exploring emotional memory

Workshop 2 built on themes emanating from the first workshop concerning memory, play and dementia and comprised a series of activities designed to stimulate conversation around *emotional* memory. The activities included: 1) *smelly pots* which provided insights into olfactory sensory stimulation and memory, 2) *dressing up* which explored visual/embodied sensory stimulation and memory and finally 3) *pass the parcel* which stimulated dialogue around laughter, fun and games.

1) Smelly Pots

In this activity participants were each given two screw top jars, each one containing a different smell from a range of substances including herbs and spices, cleaning chemicals, lavender, engine oil etc. Participants were seated around a large table and asked to unscrew the jar, smell the content and if willing, volunteer to share memories evoked by the contents of the jars. The smells stimulated anecdotal and emotional memories and many of the participants noted how quickly they were transported back to past

1 People living with dementia, at an early stage of the disease, have informed the initial LAUGH project case study research and people in the late stages of the disease will evaluate design prototypes yet to be developed.

experiences. They were keen to share memories of life events, stories of childhood and reminiscences of being in particular places. As participants recognised the particular smell they were able to link it with a significant past experience along with other sensory cues and emotions associated with it. Some of these memories were deep, strongly emotional and were acknowledged as having been forgotten for a very long time. Discussions took place around the importance of olfactory stimulation in rekindling deep and emotional memories. Some participants were able to share with the group very detailed memories associated with and stimulated by the particular smell. After opening a jar containing the smell of bees wax polish, one participant noted:

'I don't know what it is, but it reminds me of the school gymnasium. Very familiar.'

Another participant noted that the smell reminded her *'of a hospital bed; a drink, diabetic sweets - hospital is a big thing.'* She went on to recall a childhood visit to hospital and her mother's illness and how she had felt emotionally at the time.

There followed a discussion about the use of words stimulated by the smelly pots. Participants were invited to list and then share some of the words stimulated by the smells. One participant, an author and poet, read poems written by people living with dementia followed by a group discussion about reminiscence in dementia care and the emotional challenges and benefits of stimulating emotional memory. He described his experience of the challenges of writing poetry with people living with dementia and how he believes it can bring a person emotional release:

'Many people living with dementia have feelings that need expressing and maybe the care home setting is not allowing them to share them. This can be done through all the arts. Our society values intellectual things over emotions. Expressing feelings, positive or negative - both have positive effect.'

When asked by a participant how he encouraged the sharing of words in the poetry writing sessions he noted the importance of empathy:

'I'm not there to speak to the person, but to listen to them. Sitting on their level, engaging with them to show you are there for them. Often carers say they (people with dementia) are no longer there, but it's the way they interact with them that take it away. You need to show you are here for them, to accept everything the person living with dementia says.'

The session concluded with a brief discussion about the importance of validating the individual person with dementia and allowing them to 'express who they are' and their 'expression for play.'

2) Dressing up

Participants were invited to watch a short video about contagious laughter. This was intended to relax them prior to the second activity session, which involved

Figure 1. Smelly pots: writing words associated with the smell.

dressing up. Researchers were aware that some participants might be self-conscious and find the activity challenging so the laughter video was used to stimulate a light hearted, playful atmosphere in which it was hoped participants would willingly engage and then share their thoughts. The research team acknowledges that by influencing the emotional tone of the session an emotional bias was introduced. However, the intention was not to gauge emotional experience per se, but to encourage participants to be sufficiently relaxed that they could engage and reflect on, their responses to the playful activity. The aim of showing the video was to communicate to the group that they were being given permission to be playful (Rogerson, Treadaway, et al. 2013). While the majority of the group appeared to enjoy the activity the influence of the researchers' presence must also be acknowledged; participants may have felt under pressure to 'please' and perform for the sake of the research. This subjectivity and bias in the study is acknowledged.

Participants were invited to rummage in two large bags of dressing up clothes, hats and accessories and select some items to wear that stimulated memories of a particularly happy point in their life. The selection of items of clothing and how they were worn created a great amount of laughter and conversation. Photographs were taken of each member of the group and a 'Personae' card completed which captured preferences of individuals at the chosen happy/favourite point in life. The researchers made an assumption that a favourite point in life would also be happy and this was confirmed by participant responses. The card asked each participant to complete the following sentences under the title of: 'A time when...'

1. I wore...
2. I listened to music by....
3. At the cinema/TV I watched...
4. My ambitions were...

Figure 2. Examples of participants' Personae Cards.

5. My idol was....
6. The food I liked eating was....
7. I lived in....
8. This point in my life made me feel....

Figure 2 shows examples of two personae cards. Once completed, participants were invited to share the information they had written on them with the group. A discussion followed about why these periods of life had been selected as instances stimulating positive emotion and the role of sensory stimulation in these memories.

In the discussion that followed, participants noted that the 'Props (dressing up clothes) were the triggers' for memories and another participant noted:

'The process takes away the fear. Allows a space to reminisce. The 'doing' of the activity reinforced a space to reminisce. Gave permission.'

One participant commented:

I picked this as it was the only prop that triggered a memory. The danger is getting channeled into one memory as that's all that is triggered by the prop. The prop reduced it to one memory but the conversation triggered more.....

The default option was 'I can't think of anything', but the activity forced me to think of something.'

Figure 3. Dressing up as a princess (left).

In addition, the props provided a deeply embodied and sensory experience. One person described how *'the dress up provoked the period chosen. I had a genuine feeling of being a princess.'*

On reflecting how this might apply to caring for people living with late stage dementia it was noted that *'props facilitate communication'* and that *'When people visit relatives, they bring photos and props to spark conversation. It is quite difficult otherwise.'*

Most participants were eager to engage with the activity but a small minority of the group found the session very challenging. Reasons for this included embarrassment, a feeling of coercion and a lack of interest in engaging in this type of play. Those who were eager to engage with the activity found themselves transported to a different time and sense of self, for example, one participant became a magician another a princess (Figure 3). The majority of the group remembered childhood experiences or those of their children. One participant reflected:

'No one wanted to be an adult. It's all about childhood or our children.' When a participant who had been reticent to join in challenged this, various members of the group noted that many of the comments written on the Personae cards concerned *safety*, the excitement of early life and potential of what the future might bring. This was evidenced in comments such as: *'I felt content, exhilarated, safe and 'cool''; 'I felt secure'; 'I was a young child, I felt happy'; and 'I felt very happy, safe and excited.'*

Music was a common theme that emerged as having great significance and discussion then focused on the importance of music in stimulating positive emotion within dementia care. The group shared anecdotes of music related experiences with people living with late stage dementia such as people who had lost spoken language but who were able to continue to sing with words or could be stirred to dance on hearing particular significant types of music. A strong relationship between music and emotion was noted by many of the participants and the ways it provides an alternative way of connecting and communicating was discussed:

'Music is a way of connecting emotionally, positive responses. A connection with somebody through music when they find it difficult to connect with people in other ways.' It provides 'Mutual connection'.

Key themes that were raised following the dressing up activity included: vulnerability in relation to playfulness, the need for feelings of safety and the use of props and music to stimulate emotional memory. The final activity brought together these themes: it involved the use of music and props to challenge participants' willingness to be playful and an opportunity to reflect on their feelings of vulnerability.

3) *Pass the Parcel*

This activity involved playing the well-known party game in which a prize is wrapped in layers of paper, each layer containing a forfeit to challenge the person who had unwrapped it as the music stopped. Forfeits included memory challenges such as: 'name the seven dwarfs', 'describe how to boil an egg' and performative activities such as 'pat your head and rub your tummy' and 'balancing biscuits on noses' (Figure 4). The overall winner of the game is the person who unwraps the present in the final layer of paper. This activity created a great deal of emotional expression in body language, facial expression and verbally. Lively music was played as the parcel was passed around the table. Both positive and negative emotions were expressed such as anticipation and excitement when passing the parcel around, fear when discovering a forfeit and joy when receiving a reward. The activity generated lively banter, conversation and much laughter.

Researchers began changing (simplifying or making easier) the requirements of the forfeits ad hoc, to mitigate participants' feelings of embarrassment and to reduce stress. Other members of the group made helpful contributions and there was a sense of camaraderie in helping the individual execute the challenge. Any attempt to complete the forfeit was rewarded with group praise, laughter, clapping and smiles.

The Pass the Parcel activity raised a number of negative issues around feelings of vulnerability, embarrassment and lack of confidence. It was noted that in order to have fun, participants had to be prepared to be vulnerable, make mistakes, appear foolish and let people laugh at them. In a loving, closely connected social group, such as a family setting, this is easier to achieve than in more socially stressed situations with people who are unfamiliar. Moments of joy also occurred as the group responded supportively to help an individual achieve the forfeit and then to congratulate them (clap, cheer, smile, laugh) once the challenge had been completed. It was also noted that when children play this game they are more goal oriented and less concerned with humiliation by their peers. By contrast, in the activity described here, the focus was on participation and performance rather than winning the prize.

Following the activity, participants were divided into three groups and asked to note on a flip chart the things that promote fun, laughter and humour and

Figure 4. Forfeits in pass the parcel: participants balancing biscuits on noses.

how this experience might differ for someone with dementia. A number of themes were identified including:

- *Embarrassment: the sharing of embarrassing experiences to promote empathy and connection*
- *Slapstick humour: being made to look foolish e.g. falling on a banana skin which reflect personal mistakes and accidental breaches of social conformity*
- *Children and childhood tales: portrayal of naivety and innocence*
- *Sea-side or bawdy humour: suggestion of risky, sexual or non politically correct behaviour*
- *Basic word play: using metaphor, simile, rhythm and rhyme*
- *Dressing up: embodied visual humour, including becoming another, changed identity or incongruous visual behaviour*
- *Dancing: moving in a way that is inconsistent with social expectations*

It was noted that people with dementia sometimes are less inhibited or constrained by social expectations of conformity and so may be amused spontaneously by some incidents, words, actions that would be considered impolite by social convention.

Discussion

A number of themes related to positive emotion and memory arose from analysis of the data gathered during the workshop activities. These included: the use of sensory triggers and props to stimulate emotional memory; the need for emotional and playful expression; self-perception and perception by others and how this relates to positive feelings of social connectivity.

Sensory triggers and props to stimulate emotional memory

People living with dementia continue to experience emotional memory, that is the memory of the feelings associated with an event, rather than the facts about what happened (Zeisel, 2011). Using cues around those types of memories, for example favourite clothing, textures, pictures, foods and songs, it is possible to

positively support how people feel and respond in that moment (Treadaway and Kenning). Positive moments of past experiences can be rekindled through nostalgic reminiscing (Batcho, Nave, & DaRin, 2011). Childhood memories in particular, are recalled and positive feelings generated as a result of experiencing sensory triggers (Boren, 2013). Those expert participants, who work directly with people with dementia, confirmed this.

In the workshop, participants were able to reflect on their own personal experiences and give examples of ways in which poetry, music and the arts are able to stimulate emotional memory for people living with dementia. It was acknowledged by the group that rekindled emotions are not always positive and that current care practice tends to inhibit rather than promote emotional expression. Olfactory senses are able to rapidly reinstate memories of places and events and this, combined with conversation with others, can stimulate associative thinking and remembering. Music, like smell, can also transport an individual to past experiences very quickly and can impact on the ability to remember words when verbal communication is limited or lost. It can also stimulate rhythm and body movement that help a person feel good, such as dancing, clapping and tapping.

There was a consensus that emotional expression should be a vital constituent of dementia care and that stimulating positive emotional memory can enhance the subjective wellbeing of people with dementia.

Emotional and playful expression

The challenge in this design research is to understand ways in which positive emotions can be stimulated for people with late stage dementia using playful objects. Playfulness is a fundamental and vital way in which human beings engage in fun, pleasure and laughter, not only in childhood but also throughout life (Rogerson et al., 2013). *Fun* and *play* are considered both appropriate and acceptable in children and regarded as valid vehicles for childhood self-expression, learning and positive emotional connection. Despite many decades of research findings affirming play in adulthood, (M. Csikszentmihalyi, 1990; Deci & Ryan, 1987; Proyer, 2013; Starbuck & Webster, 1991) society at large still seems to regard playfulness as incompatible with serious adult activities (Kane, 2005). Toys, such as dolls and teddy bears, are used in dementia care, however they are often considered infantilising and inappropriate by relatives and some health professionals (Mitchell & O'Donnell, 2013).

Nevertheless, there is research evidence that playful activities in later life have positive benefits to wellbeing. Waldman-Levi et al. (2015) contend that playfulness contributes to 'adaptability and resilience in life, especially in later life,' (Waldman-Levi et al, 2015, p. 5). Although fun is largely intrinsic and internally motivated, socially focused playful activities bring external rewards including conversation and laughter. Ryan & Deci (2000) contend that internally motivated activities result in 'greater persistence, more positive self-perceptions, and better quality of engagement' (Ryan & Deci, 2000 pp. 60-61).

Objects that encourage independent playful interaction provide intrinsic reward by fostering self-directed interaction and re-igniting feelings of efficacy and interest in the world.

The playful activities experienced by workshop participants' stimulated discussion about ways in which people living with dementia experience positive emotions through props (reminiscence material), music, dance and creative activities, many of which take place in a social context.

Social connectivity

People living with dementia have a heightened sensitivity to emotion and this can lead to communication that is largely receptive and dependent on the moods of others (Logsdon, Gibbons, McCurry, & Teri, 2005). Although emotions and emotional memory continue to be experienced, it can be difficult for a person with dementia to express what they are feeling verbally and with clarity. Workshop participants agreed that greater opportunities are needed for people with dementia to express their emotions as this can help build resilience and positivity. Since verbal expression can be problematic, activities that encourage non-verbal emotional expression can become a way of sharing, understanding and build positive feelings of happiness and comfort (Treadaway, Kenning, & Coleman, 2015).

In the workshop, participants engaged in eye contact, touch, laughter and physical connection with others. Laughter and smiles have evolved and create emotional connection between people – they are contagious and have a positive impact on both mental and physical health. These forms of high quality connections with others enhance health and wellbeing, '*...positive emotions provide benefits - each... broadens your mind-set and builds your resourcefulness*' (Fredrickson, 2014, p10). Fredrickson (2014, p19) equates these high quality moments of connection between people, which she terms *positivity resonance*, as moments of love. Evidence from the workshop described in this paper reveals ways in which emotional experiences and memories can elicit positive emotion that can be shared through empathic high quality connections.

Conclusion

Designing specifically for connectedness, to encourage social connections, will be a powerful tool to support the ageing population (Wildevuur et al., 2013). Designs that can stimulate moments of high quality connection between people will help them experience and share positive emotion. The need is for playful, personally significant designs that are amusing, fun and have potential to stimulate social connections. Findings from this study suggest that moments of positive emotion can be shared socially when people feel relaxed and safe. Empathy and reciprocity enable potentially difficult or embarrassing experiences to be transformed into positive moments of humour and fun, shared through smiles and laughter.

In this workshop, participants were given permission to play and encouraged to experience positive

emotions. Their reflections on personal experiences of positive emotion during the workshop, and the perceived relevance of this to people living with dementia with whom they work, will be used to inform the design of playful objects for people with late stage dementia in the subsequent phases of the LAUGH project. The key considerations arising from this study that will be used to inform the design phase include the following:

- *Props and sensory triggers are useful ways of stimulating associations and rekindling emotional memories*
- *Wearable props can enable a person to explore their sense of self so that they are seen and can feel differently about themselves and others*
- *Smell and music were identified as being particularly significant sensory tools to rapidly elicit emotional memory*
- *Visual and tactile sensory cues can prompt deep memories and associations but the triggers for these are highly personal and related to individual preferences and experiences*

Design concepts will be informed by the knowledge generated by this study but will not necessarily relate physically to the props and activities used in the workshop described. The subsequent design phase of the LAUGH project proposes to generate new types of objects that can stimulate positive emotion and moments of connection for people living with late stage dementia. The intention is to explore new materials and technologies that can enable greater personalisation, extend sensory experiences and facilitate social connectivity.

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The effects of enlarged words in text messages: Look clearer, but less premium

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Abstract This study explored the effects of enlarged words in text messages on receivers' affective judgment of the contents. In order empirically to investigate the effects, we conducted two experiments: One was a preliminary study to observe general user responses to enlarged text messages, and the other one was a survey to measure emotional responses of users when contexts of text messaging were specified. Based on the results, we revealed positive and negative aspects of using enlarging words as a nonverbal cue in text message communication.

Keywords *Computer-mediated communication, Text messaging, Font size, Enlarged words, User experience*

Introduction

People use a lot of nonverbal cues in face-to-face conversation such as body movements, eye gazes, and vocal inflections in order to convey perceptual information. In computer-mediated communication (CMC), however, nonverbal aspects are not fully presented, especially in text-based channels (McKenna & Bargh, 2000).

Although the number of possible nonverbal cues are limited, people still have a desire to express their latent thoughts and impressions within text-based communications. Such desires have induced atypical uses of text messaging (Grinter & Eldridge, 2003; Tu, 2002). For instance, Kalman and Gergle (Kalman & Gergle, 2014) have found that letter repetitions often emulate nonverbal cues. Studies by Darics (Darics, 2013) and Tu (Tu, 2002) have also supported the non-standard use of texts as a means for nonverbal communication. In order to promote the nonverbal aspects of text-based communications, several approaches have been made. The study by Brumberger [3] has suggested typeface functions as a strong nonverbal cue that grants a personality to the texts. Bringing motion into texts was one of the most frequent approaches (Bodine & Pignol, 2003; Lee, Jun, Forlizzi, & Hudson, 2006; Yeo, 2008), and the results showed that kinetic typography enhances the emotional experience of users in text-based communications. Although these investigations have demonstrated the advantages of using nonverbal communication tools to deliver emotional information, such tools have not yet been widely used in real life due to their complexity and technical gaps.

In this regard, we focused on font size, which can be manipulated easily within current text-based communication channels. To the best of our knowledge, font size has not been examined as a nonverbal cue, even though its effects on readability

and usability have been studied frequently (Boyarski, Neuwirth, Forlizzi, & Regli, 1998; Darroch, Goodman, Brewster, & Gray, 2005). Hence, we investigated the effect of font size within the context of text messaging, which is one of the most prevailing forms of text-based communication.

In addition, rather than examining how senders use the font size as a nonverbal cue, we investigated how receivers perceive this cue. Earlier works related to nonverbal aspects in text messages have mainly focused on strategies of conveying emotional information from the perspective of senders (Hancock, Landrigan, & Silver, 2007; Lee et al., 2006). Since the nonverbal aspects have high possibility of being misinterpreted (Derks, Fischer, & Bos, 2008), it is significant to consider the perspective of receivers to explore the effects of font size on perceiving and interpreting text messages.

The goal of this study is to explore the possibilities of font size, and especially the use of enlarged words, as a nonverbal cue in text messaging. With this specification, we have following three aims: 1) To understand the comprehensive user experience in relation to the use of enlarged words within text messages, 2) To identify the influence of the context of the text messages (e.g. relationship of sender-receiver, contents of messages) upon the perception of enlarged words, and 3) To suggest design implications that summarize the perceptions of enlarged words in text messages. With these aims, we first performed a preliminary study to understand the comprehensive perceptions of users who received text messages. Based on this preliminary exploration, we proceeded to the main study, which investigates the influence of other factors on the perception of enlarged words. At last, we summarized the findings into design implications.

Preliminary exploration

As stated previously, there is little information available on the emotional effects of enlarged words in text messages. Hence, we conducted an explorative study in order to understand the comprehensive user experience in relation to enlarged words. Six individuals were recruited for the study. They were graduate students who were studying interaction design and were familiar with using text messages. Firstly, we collected 60 chat rooms (10 chat rooms per person) that were recently activated from the messaging applications on each participant's smartphone (e.g. iMessage). From the samples, we selected 10 representative chat rooms, which were frequently appeared across different participants. Half of them were interactive dialogues with unfamiliar friends, a colleague or a family member. The other half consists of a streamline of notice messages from a restaurant, an online shopping mall, or service providers.

Two of researchers who were studying interaction design modified the text chats by enlarging 1 to 3 words of a message within a chat. They selected words which reflect the major atmosphere or the main topic of the text chats. Once the words to be enlarged were decided, we made iterative trials to identify the font size of enlarged words. Through these trials, the font size for the enlarged words was set at twice the size of the normal text. This provided an apparent contrast between the two without compromising the legibility (Figure 1).

We presented the 10 pairs of text chats to each participant as images of 750x1334 resolution and conducted a semi-structured interview with these stimuli. During the interview sessions, we mainly focused on the feelings and needs of receivers in relation to the enlarged words. Participants were asked to verbalize how they felt about the text messages with enlarged words in comparison with the normal ones. They were then asked to spell out the words that needed to be enlarged from their perspective as receivers. We made a note of the verbal descriptions and analyzed the notes by classifying the nouns and adjectives that participants had utilized. The results provided two insights regarding the perceptions of enlarged words within text messages.

Enlarged words evoke emotional responses beyond the contents of messages

We collected descriptions that participants used to express their feelings and thoughts about enlarged words. Many of them were related to affective and emotional responses. For instance, one participant described an enlarged word as an "emoji" and stated that "it looks like it's speaking out loud". Another participant mentioned that the contents sounded "reliable" when the due date (e.g. January 29) of medical examination notice was enlarged. Contrary to these positive responses, the enlarged words sometimes evoke negative emotions. When the amount of money was enlarged within a conversation between friends, participants often perceive it as heartless. Overall, participants felt that there was a reason that certain words were selectively enlarged within a

Figure 1. Comparison of normal-sized words and an enlarged word in text messages.

message, and tried to identify the intention of the sender. This process frequently evoked emotional responses beyond the written contents of the text messages.

Emphasize information, enhance emotion

In relation to the needs of enlarged words as a receiver, two distinctive perspectives emerged. One perspective was related to the emphasis of key information provided in a message. For instance, the due date of a health checkup and the license number of a vehicle were often mentioned. In these cases, participants wanted to grasp the important information quickly and efficiently (e.g. "I can see the essential part of the texts at a glance"). The other perspective was about the degree of perceived emotion. Particularly in apologetic and appreciative contexts, participants frequently associated the enlarged word with the sincerity of emotion (e.g. "I feel that the emotion [of the sender] is emphasized"). This indicates that receivers may expect that senders are expressing their attitudes and emotions by enlarging particular words.

Main study

Through the preliminary exploration, we found that both positive and negative emotions can be raised by enlarging certain words. We also identified that people wanted to enlarge different words depending on the main theme of the chats. In order to investigate the effect of enlarged words in specific contexts and how such enlarged words are perceived, we conducted a main study as described below.

Experimental Design

Independent variables

We set three independent variables with two levels for each: Size of Word, Type of Communication, and Contents of the Enlarged Word. Figure 2 illustrates the experimental design with examples of text messages.

- Size of Word. This variable is fundamental for investigating the general effect of 1) Enlarged words in text messages as compared to 2) Normal-sized text messages. We maintained the same conditions for font sizes and screen resolution that were used in the preliminary study.
- Type of Communication. The text chats collected from the participants of preliminary study were

		Contents of Enlarged Words			
		Emotion	Information	Emotion	Information
Size of Word	Normal	aaarrrrghhhh!!! so tired	student card or credit card?	... appreciated if you get your...	... due date : January 29
	Enlarged	aaarrrrghhhh!!! so tired	student card or credit card?	... appreciated if you get your...	... due date : January 29
		Two-way (usually in dialogue)		One-way (usually in notice)	
		Type of Communication			

Figure 2. Experimental design of the main study with examples of text messages.

divided into two categories regarding their text chat type. One type of chat was 1) A two-way communication (usually in dialogue) that consisted of an interactive conversation between people, and the other was 2) A one-way communication (usually in notice) such as an announcement or an advertisement.

- Contents of Enlarged Word. Reflecting the needs of receivers that were revealed in the preliminary study, we investigated the effects of the content that enlarged words delivered. We made two variations for each message: one variation enlarged words that expressed 1) Emotion, and the other enlarged words that expressed 2) Information.

In order to examine the effects of the *Size of Word*, pairwise comparison was used to compare the perceptions of enlarged words against those of the normal messages. For examining the effects of the *Type of Communication* and the *Contents of Enlarged Words*, we devised a 2x2 within group design. We prepared three different text chats for each of Two-way (dialogue) and One-way (notice) communication. After enlarging words with different

contents in each chat we had a total of 12 stimuli (Table 1).

Dependent variables

The preliminary exploration revealed that people make affective judgments on the enlarged words beyond the given contents of text chats. In order to measure the degree of emotions evoked by enlarging certain words, we decided to use 13 adjectives that convey positive emotions. The 13 adjectives were originated from two sources. One source was AttrakDiff (Hassenzahl, Burmester, & Koller, 2003), which is a widely validated tool for evaluating user experience, and we selected 7 adjectives from the tool - *Attractive, Clear, Human, Inventive, Premium, Professional, Simple* - that seemed to be matched with the context in which the text message was received. The other source was the emotional terms that were collected during the preliminary study. We chose six adjectives - *Careful, Familiar, Young, Natural, Practical, Reliable* -, which provided interesting descriptions about the latent meanings of enlarged words. Using these 13 adjectives, we made a survey question for each stimuli. Figure 3 shows a sample of survey question to rates the relative attractiveness of enlarged words within a notice

Table 1. Summary of 12 stimuli used in the main study.

Type of Communication	Relationship	Contents of enlarged words	Enlarged words within a message (typed in bold)
Two-way (usually in dialogue)	Close friends	Emotion	AHHH!! So tired
		Information	ID card or Credit card?
	Couple	Emotion	love u MORE~
		Information	See you after Three Days~!
	Family	Emotion	Thank you so much!! mum
		Information	Just give me \$5
One-way (usually in notice)	Hospital — customer	Emotion	We will be appreciated if you get your health checkup as soon as possible
		Information	Sign up Due date for Health Checkup: January 29
	Restaurant — customer	Emotion	We hope you will win the great prize of this event!
		Information	(...) great chance to get a New Laptop and a New Smartphone
	Call-Taxi service — customer	Emotion	Thank you for using our service
		Information	Your HanbitCall ride will arrive soon. Car Number : 5870

message from a hospital.

Procedure

We recruited 32 graduate and undergraduate students who were familiar with text messaging (15 males and 17 females, 24.94 years old on average). We showed participants 12 pairs of text chats one by one and asked them to rate the relative scores of enlarged words compared to the normal ones using 13 different adjectives. Accordingly, each participant answered a total of 156 questions (12 pairs x 13 adjectives). Ratings were measured using a 5-point Likert scale from “not at all (-2)” to “very much (+2)”. Since all of 13 adjectives convey positive emotions, the negative ratings indicated that enlarged words had a bad influence upon the perception of receivers.

Results of the main study

We devised two statistical methods to analyze the data, a one-sample t-test and a within-group two-way ANOVA. A one-sample t-test was conducted to compare the ratings of 13 enlarged words from four different contexts (52 cases) with the normal-sized text messages, which were regarded as having a rating of 0. A within-group two-way ANOVA was conducted to examine the effects of the *Type of Communication* and the *Contents of Enlarged Words*.

Effects of size of word in general

As shown in Table 2, the results of the one-sample t-test showed that there were significant differences in ratings in 31 cases out of 52 ($p < .05$). Among 31 cases, 22 enlarged words received higher ratings than normal-sized ones, which indicate positive responses, while 9 cases received lower ratings, which indicate negative responses. Interestingly, the uses of enlarged words were perceived *less Premium* but *Clearer* regardless of its context. Except these two emotional terms, the effects of enlarged words vary depending on the combinations of *Type of Communication* and the *Contents of Enlarged Words*. In order to investigate the effects of these factors in more detail, we proceeded to the next analysis.

Figure 3. Sample of survey question.

Effects of size of word depending on contexts

Table 2 summarizes the results of two-way ANOVA. It showed that the *Type of Communication* only had effects on the perception of 5 adjectives, while the *Contents of Enlarged Words* had effects on 12 adjectives out of 13. This indicates that the *Contents of Enlarged Words* have a broader influence on the affective judgment of receivers than the *Type of Chat*. Participants made more discrete judgments depending on whether emotional words are enlarged or informational words are enlarged than whether the text chat is a two-way(dialogue) or a one-way(notice).

For instance, the degree of *Humaneness* was significantly higher when emotional words were enlarged in both dialogues and notices. In contrast, the degree of *Practicality* and *Reliability* were significantly higher when informational words were enlarged in both dialogues and notices. These three adjectives were examples of emotions that mainly

Table 2. Mean differences between enlarged words and normal-sized ones.

* Statistically significant results ($p < .05$)

Dependent variables	Dialogue-Emotion	Notice-Emotion	Dialogue-Information	Notice-Information
Attractive	0.74*	0.20	-0.14	0.46
Careful	-0.43*	-0.41*	-0.01	0.18
Clear	0.72*	0.30*	1.00*	1.22*
Familiar	0.79*	0.23	-0.02	0.18
Humane	1.02*	0.59*	-0.09	0.16
Inventive	0.53*	-0.07	0.11	0.30*
Natural	0.64*	0.05	-0.19	0.35*
Practical	0.32*	0.07	0.79*	1.18*
Premium	-0.89*	-0.81*	-0.78*	-0.41*
Professional	-0.65*	-0.62*	-0.26	0.27*
Reliable	-0.02	-0.25*	0.24*	0.57*
Simple	0.26	0.24	0.51*	1.00*
Young	0.78*	-0.01	-0.09	-0.09

affected by *Contents of Enlarged Words*.

Beyond the main effects of the *Type of Communication* and the *Contents of Enlarged Words*, interesting interaction effects were observed upon the perception of 12 of the 13 adjectives. This indicates that people perceived differently depending on which contents were enlarged in which type of text chat. To be specific, participants perceived the enlarged emotional words in dialogues and enlarged informational words in notices more *Attractive, Inventive, and Natural*.

Implications for practice

The results of preliminary and main studies shown that using enlarged words in text messages can be used as a nonverbal cue that evokes affective judgments. Depending on context, however, the perception of receivers could be both positive and negative. In this regard, we summarized the findings in order to make them applicable in practical fields such as instant messenger applications, automatic text-based announcement systems, viral marketing, and so on. Figure 4 shows the summary of findings graphically.

Using enlarged words in dialogues (Q1, Q4)

Compared to the notice-type chats, using enlarged words in dialogues has more advantages. Even in dialogues, however, the messages could be perceived differently depending on the contents of the enlarged words. Hence, the use of enlarged words in dialogues should be considered carefully depending on the aim of the message. For example, enlarging the emotional words can help to make the message appear more humane and attractive, even if it may look careless and unprofessional (Q1). By contrast, enlarging informational words can help to make the message appear more practical and reliable (Q4). Recently, increasing numbers of IoT systems ("Introducing LG HomeChat,") are devising dialogue-type communications as a way of controlling devices. In such applications, the user experience could be enhanced by enlarging appropriate words depending on the purpose of communication.

Figure 4. Positive and negative effects of using enlarged words depending on contexts.

Using enlarged words in notices (Q2, Q3)

In the meantime, use of text messages to send advertisements and announcements is common, and such text messages mainly focus on conveying information rather than emotions. In this manner, the positive effects revealed in Q3 supports the effective use of enlarged words in notices sent via text-based communications. For example, the attractiveness and reliability of notice messages can be improved by enlarging the information to be delivered. However, enlarging the emotional words in notices may damage the sincerity and genuineness of the message, especially when it expresses emotions such as appreciation and apology (Q2).

Conclusion

In this paper, we have investigated how enlarged words affect to the emotional interpretation of text

Table 3. Results of two-way ANOVA test. * Statistically significant results ($p < .05$)

Dependent variables	Main effect of Type of Communication	Main effect of Contents of Enlarged Words	Interaction effect
Attractive	F(1,31) = 0.05	F(1,31) = 5.03*	F(1,31) = 30.90*
Careful	F(1,31) = 1.52	F(1,31) = 35.06*	F(1,31) = 1.18*
Clear	F(1,31) = 1.65	F(1,31) = 24.15*	F(1,31) = 7.71*
Familiar	F(1,31) = 3.53	F(1,31) = 11.88*	F(1,31) = 17.68*
Humane	F(1,31) = 0.87	F(1,31) = 35.96*	F(1,31) = 14.46*
Inventive	F(1,31) = 6.31*	F(1,31) = 0.04	F(1,31) = 28.58*
Natural	F(1,31) = 0.05	F(1,31) = 5.01*	F(1,31) = 19.11*
Practical	F(1,31) = 0.51	F(1,31) = 55.08*	F(1,31) = 6.43*
Premium	F(1,31) = 8.61*	F(1,31) = 7.97*	F(1,31) = 6.98*
Professional	F(1,31) = 8.61*	F(1,31) = 44.36*	F(1,31) = 8.79*
Reliable	F(1,31) = 0.41	F(1,31) = 28.98*	F(1,31) = 11.28*
Simple	F(1,31) = 11.37*	F(1,31) = 24.42*	F(1,31) = 4.64*
Young	F(1,31) = 8.74*	F(1,31) = 13.16*	F(1,31) = 23.15*

Figure 5. Positive effects of using enlarged words with exemplar cases.

messages. In the preliminary study we examined the possibilities of enlarging words to emphasize information and enhance emotions beyond the contents of text messages. Our findings indicate that enlarged words in text messages evoke emotional responses, and such response can be both positive and negative depending on the *Type of Communication* and the *Contents of Enlarged Words*. Figure 5 shows the examples of enlarged words in specific contexts that illustrates the positive and distinctive effects for each case. Although each context has benefits, enlarged emotions in dialogue and enlarged information in notice have greater advantages in perceptions of receivers. These findings may enhance the nonverbal aspects of text-based communications in various fields such as instant messengers, automatic text announcements, and so on. In conclusion, the first contribution of the study is to explore the possibility of using the enlarged word in various text message contexts to enrich the text-based communication. The second contribution is to provide new design opportunities of using the enlarged word in text messages for interaction designers and design researchers.

In our future work, we plan to study the intentions of using enlarged words in text-based communication, so that we may provide implications for using enlarged words as a nonverbal cue in text-based communication.

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Perfect days. A benevolent calendar to take back your time

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Abstract “Time poverty” touches upon a tension between the ever increasing time demands of work and the time needed for people to engage in further, intrinsically meaningful, wellbeing-enhancing activities. At the heart of this drama is the digital calendar. While often only seen as a useful and quite innocent tool, its functionality and representation subtly enforces certain ways of dealing with time. To counter this, we developed the concept of a benevolent calendar: *Perfect Days* explicitly cares about the wellbeing-oriented activities of its user. In a study with five quite busy individuals over three weeks, we found that the majority experienced *Perfect Days* as positive and acknowledged its goal to change time use for the better. After a phase of irritation, participants felt more aware of their personal time use, adopted new wellbeing-enhancing activities, and in part even already internalized these activities.

Keywords Wellbeing, Experience design, Time use, Digital calendar, Productivity tools

Time use, wellbeing, and the digital calendar

Subjective wellbeing is the consequence of having enjoyable and meaningful experiences in everyday life. Such experiences result from engaging in activities (Lyubomirsky, Sheldon, & Schkade, 2005), which fulfill psychological needs (Ryan & Deci, 2000). For this, sufficient time is of essence. Unfortunately, many people suffer from what can be best described as “time poverty”. Feelings that “one’s life has been too rushed” or that “there have not been enough minutes in the day” are common and related to reduced wellbeing (Kasser & Sheldon, 2008). Kroll and Pokutta (2013) used data about how much people enjoy particular day-to-day activities to create a “perfect day”, that is, a scheduling which would maximize wellbeing. It assumes 16 hours (=960 minutes) available per day and recommends to spend, for example, 106 minutes with intimate relations, 82 minutes with socializing, 78 minutes with relaxing, 75 minutes with eating, 73 minutes with praying/meditating and 68 minutes with exercising, but only 36 minutes with working. Wryly, the authors note that “somebody who only works for 36 min each day is of course most likely to have problems making ends meet. [...] Hence, the optimal day schedule may be more realistically applied to a Sunday rather than a Monday” (Kroll & Pokutta, 2013, p. 215). This blatantly points at peoples’ constant need to negotiate between time for work and all the other activities they require to be happy (i.e., maintaining work-life balance). This is not easy, since “busyness” seems to have become a deeply internalized moral value (at least in the USA). At the same time people experience conflicts, anxiety and guilt concerning the way they use their time mostly in favor of work (Leshed & Sengers, 2011).

Our tools of time, clocks and calendars, play an important role in this daily drama, because they heavily influence the way we perceive, use and

experience time (e.g., Lindley, 2015; Leshed & Sengers, 2011, p. 912). Take the lack of representation of free, personal time in work calendars. Currently, in a work calendar, free time is just “unused”, undedicated time. The implication is clear. If a calendar is full, one is a busy, hard-working person; if the calendar is empty, one is not. An empty calendar is a luxury; a full calendar a necessity. The digital calendar not only mirrors societal or economic trends. It also enforces them by shaping our perception and use of time.

Obviously, calendars can take many different forms (Buzzo & Merendino, 2015), each ripe with its own meanings. In the present paper, we empirically explore the idea of a benevolent calendar, designed to support people in taking back (at least some) of their time to increase wellbeing. We place this in the context of designing for wellbeing (e.g., Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013; Hassenzahl et al., 2013).

Specifically, we first “constructed” a perfect *work* day by prompting people to explicitly allocate time to meaningful personal and social activities on a work day, such as “putting the children to bed”, “playing music”, “exercising”, or “meditating”. Of course, the resulting perfect day was idealized. However, it remained dominated by work, while at the same time people seemed to more consciously consider how much time to spend with work and what to do best in their free time. We then transformed the individual perfect days into a set of daily calendar entries. These were added automatically to the already used calendars. The design rationale was simple: The calendar extension aimed at taking over work time and replacing it with well-being time by using the codes and habits borrowed from work. Undedicated time is now not just free to be filled with more work, but already occupied with personally relevant activities. By confronting its user with their own idealized

behaviour, the calendar was supposed to create friction and to prompt the conscious renegotiation of time and activities (Hassenzahl & Laschke, 2015; Laschke, Diefenbach, & Hassenzahl, 2015). To make the superimposed activities more distinguishable, we gave them unusual labels. They consisted of a verb (i.e., an activity) followed by direct speech related to personal goals (e.g. *sleep – “now off to bed!”* for a person, who has problems in calling it a day and getting enough sleep). We tried to let these activities appear more like time-based suggestions than fixed calendar entries, to signal sympathy for the difficulty of implementing the activities in everyday life. In the following, we report detailed quantitative and qualitative findings from a three week field exploration of Perfect Days with five people.

Perfect Days in the wild

Participants, procedure, and analysis

A convenience sample of five individuals participated in the study (3 female, ages: 27, 35, 40, 41, 45 years). They were recruited by members of the research team. The crucial requirement for being included as a participant was a busy work schedule and the routine use of a digital calendar in everyday (work) life.

Table 1 shows brief characterization of the participants. All were quite busy, with most of them (except P4) feeling not entirely happy with their current use of time. Their relationship with the calendar was mostly bittersweet: It appears to be a necessary, but sometimes harsh master.

The study started with an approximately thirty-minute interview conducted via phone or *Skype* by the third author. Some introductory remarks and a general

conversation about individual time use and the role of the digital calendar served as ice-breaker and provided some background information about the participants (Table 1). The interviewer then asked the participant to reconstruct a *typical* work day by creating prototypical calendar events (e.g., meetings, work, lunch) and placing them on a typical 24-hour grid (Kahneman, Krueger, Schkade, Schwarz, & Stone, 2004). After this, the participants were asked to imagine a *perfect* working day and were prompted to include activities, which would improve their wellbeing, but do not seem to fit into their day. The interviewer proposed thinking about activities from the categories sleep, meals, personal hygiene, social contacts, physical activities, contemplation and maintenance/housekeeping. The resulting personal blueprint of a perfect day was again drawn up on a 24-hour grid.

We then created a *Perfect Day* .ics-file for each participant, which contained *only* the selected personal activities, e.g., “12:00 lunch” (meal) or “20:00 going for a drink with my husband” (social contacts). The .ics was emailed to the participants together with instructions of how to import the file into their main calendar. After the import, the personal perfect day activities became regular entries for the next three weeks.

Participants were instructed to use their calendar as usual. We explicitly told them to adapt perfect day activities to the particular requirements of the day at hand, i.e., to delete the activities, if they did not find the time or to move activities, if done earlier or later etc. We asked them to make sure that for each day the calendar most closely matched what they actually did.

Table 1. Brief characterizations of the participants.

Participant	Time use and calendars
P1, female, 41 married, two children, employed manager	P1 works from home. She feels challenged by balancing time for her work, her family, and herself. For her, time has a negative connotation since the lack of it seems so apparent. On weekdays, nearly 100% of her time has to be planned in a relatively fixed manner. In general, she experiences the calendar as a supportive tool. Now and then, she gets annoyed, since it tends to be too full
P2, female, 35 single, self-employed	P2 works from home. The digital calendar is her most important tool, because structuring time and ensuring productivity is very important to her. She is an “expert” in using her digital calendar with all its available features. For example, she uses the calendar to keep up with social and cultural activities through different calendar subscriptions. Her relationship to the calendar is in general positive. However, now and then she can't keep it updated. The calendar ends up being not representative of how busy she really is and this tempts her to take on even more work and appointments
P3, male, 40 married, two children, university researcher	P3 works in an office. He suffers from lack of time and inflexibility. The day is heavily structured by routines, e.g., taking care of the children. Personal time is mostly in the evening, but he feels too exhausted to do something meaningful then. He describes his relationship to the calendar as a forced marriage. While it plays an important role in planning time at work, the calendar is perceived as dominant. It puts P3 under pressure and “pushes him around”. Because of this he is reluctant to use his calendar for private activities
P4, female, 27 single, doctoral candidate, self-employed	P4 works in an office and from home. Her relationship to time is quite relaxed. It all seems a matter of how to prioritize to make everything fit in. She feels a responsibility to organize her time into clear rhythms and enjoys this. She also looks for “cracks” within these structures to indulge in free time. She has a very positive relationship to her calendar. It contains both business and private activities
P5, male, 47 married, three children, employed manager	P5 works in an office. Time management and the calendar plays an important role in work, but in his private life, P5 doesn't make use of the calendar. He enjoys his works, but admits that his family does not get as much time as he wishes for. Over the years, however, he has improved the balance between his work and private life, e.g., through prioritizing. His relationship to the calendar is neither clearly negative nor positive. The calendar creates pressure, but at the same time P5 is very proficient in making the calendar work in his favour. He, for example, creates “appointments” to block time, he needs to work on a task, important to him

Participant 2 Mo - Fr	Participant 3 Mo, Tue, Thu, Fr	Wed
00:00 - 07:00 Sleep	00:00 - 06:00 Sleep	00:00 - 06:00 Sleep
07:00 - 07:15 Meditation	06:00 - 07:30 Get up & get everyone ready	06:00 - 07:30 Get up & get everyone ready
07:15 - 08:00 Start the day	08:30 - 09:30 Work but no emails yet	08:30 - 09:30 Work but no emails yet
08:00 - 08:30 Read blogs	11:45 - 12:45 Lunch	11:45 - 12:45 Lunch
08:30 - 09:00 Plan the day, start to work	16:30 - 17:30 Plan tomorrow, stop working	16:30 - 17:30 Plan tomorrow, stop working
11:30 - 12:30 Write songs, make music	18:15 - 18:45 Dinner	18:15 - 18:45 Dinner
12:30 - 13:30 Lunch	20:15 - 20:30 Tidy up	20:15 - 20:30 Tidy up
16:00 - 17:00 Practice instruments	20:30 - 22:00 Free time, hobbies	20:30 - 22:00 Work out/Running
17:00 - 17:30 Grocery shopping	22:30 - 00:00 Sleep	22:30 - 00:00 Sleep
17:30 - 18:30 Work out/Running		
18:30 - 19:30 Dinner		
21:00 - 24:00 Meet friends		

Figure 1. Example of perfect day activities and their scheduling.

At the end of the three week period, we asked participants to export the *Perfect Day* calendar and send it back. This enabled us to analyse the difference between the originally envisioned perfect day and real days. A second interview was conducted via phone or *Skype* and took place on the last day of the study phase (plus four days). The second interview was an open conversation (run by the third author) about the three-week period. The participants were prompted to talk about topics, such as how they used the Perfect Day calendar, how well it worked, if the calendar changed some of their routines, if they would like to keep on using this calendar or aspects of it.

The first interview served as introduction for the participants and was used to compile brief characterizations of the participants (Table 1). The interviews were analyzed quantitatively (Section "Findings: Activities"). The second interview was transcribed and submitted to a thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Emerging themes were discussed among authors and further refined (Section "Findings: Eight emerging themes").

Activities

Each participant defined at least one perfect day, some even more (up to three different versions for different days of the week). Of course, days differed in the number of daily activities defined. Figure 1 shows three example days from P2 and P3.

On average, the number of activities planned for a single day was 8.4, with substantial variation among participants (6.6 to 12) (Table 2). Of 8.4 activities, participants realized 5.2 per day on average (62%). Since available time on a day is finite, the more events participants planned for the more difficult it should be

to realize the ideal. However, this was not apparent: P5 (6.6 events per day) had about the same realization rate as P2 (12.0 events per day).

We correlated the relative number of realized activities for each day (real/ideal) with the order of day per person to estimate change over time (Table 2, column "change"). The results were mixed. While for P1 and P4 the percentage of realized activities did not change at all over time, P2 revealed a slightly negative, but insignificant trend to realize less activities over time. P3 and P5 revealed a positive trend, with P5 reaching statistical significance. In fact, P5 realized only 55% of activities in the first week, 58% in the second week, but 76% in the final week.

Eight emerging themes

Theme 1: Overall impression is positive

Overall, our *Perfect Day* calendar extension (PD) was received positively (all P's except P4). A prominent explanation for the positive impression was that PD

Table 2. Number of ideal and realized activities for each participant, relative frequency, and change over time.

P	Ideal per day (sum)	Realized per day (sum)	Relative	Change ^a
1	7.0 (105)	3.5 (52)	50%	-.06
2	12.0 (180)	7.7 (115)	64%	-.36
3	8.0 (120)	6.6 (96)	83%	.28
4	8.6 (129)	4.3 (65)	50%	.03
5	6.6 (99)	4.1 (62)	63%	.53*
Mean	8.4	5.2	62%	

Notes: a) Spearman's Rho; *) p<.05

helped with gaining control over personal time. P2 explained: “[...] *the best [...] was to experience that it is really not so hard to integrate all the work-unrelated activities, all the activities I really want to do, into everyday life.*” P5 said: “*A valuable support, although I did not slavishly obey.*”

An important precondition of control is insight. P3, for example, reflected that PD made him “*aware of things, about the ‘hooks and eyes’ of daily scheduling.*” It prompted the conscious negotiation of his own needs with those of others: “[...] *there is a need to coordinate with my wife, who does the baby-sitting [...], who already has an appointment? [PD helps] to make a conscious effort to integrate it [perfect day activities]*” (P3). P1 perceived the PD as especially caring. She said: “*I had this feeling, there is somebody worrying about me [laughs]. The calendar is worrying about me and this felt good [...]. A little like saying ‘Be careful to do all the things, you wanted to do’.*” And further: “*If it is in the calendar, I don’t have to choose anymore. This is good.*” Of course, P1 did not slavishly obey the calendar, too, but rather creatively responded to its prompts. However, for her PD became something active, a “thing with attitude”, while the majority of participants still emphasized its tool-like qualities.

P4 was outright negative about PD. She was annoyed, showing “reactance”. While she couldn’t quite explain this, the negative response seems to emerge from the same qualities as the positive experiences described by the others. Reactance (Brehm, 1966) is a response to perceived external restrictions of autonomy. What P1 framed positively as “caring” is experienced by P4 as an unwarranted intervention. A reason for this may be that she perceived herself as already quite thoughtful and successful in managing her time.

Theme 2: Carefully blurring the line between work time and private activities

Some participants felt reluctant to schedule their private time in a similar way to work time (see also Table 1). P4 said that through PD free time “*lost its playful lightness*” (P4). In the same vein, P3 said, while acknowledging the positive powers of PD, that it seems “*stupid to ‘clock’ off-hours, but there seems no way around it*” (P3).

Conceptually, PD tries to take over work time and to replace it with wellbeing time by using the codes and habits borrowed from work. This blurs the line between both. In a way, it spoils peoples’ ideal of free time as something being spontaneously filled with relaxing and stimulating activities. At the same time, P3 acknowledges that this ideal may be hard to attain in everyday life, since free time is likely to be “sucked-up” by contracted time. This is a tension deliberately designed into PD.

To make this more bearable, we employed a particular way of presenting activities to distinguish them from the work related entries: short funny, slightly ironic labels, which could be understood as comments made by the calendar itself. All participants experienced this as positive. P1 pointed out that “*it made very clear that this [a PD activity] is not a work appointment*”

(P1). To her, it was important that the communication was “*friendly and not lecturing*” (P1). She said: “*[PD] is just there and nicely says ‘That’s enough now’*” (P1). P2 also perceived a difference between PD activities and work entries: “*[They appear] definitely not like a meeting*” (P2). She also liked the motivational nature of the phrasing. P5 summarized: “*It stood out. I found it charming. [...] It’s a different way of thinking. The colour and the linguistic distinction helped to perceive, it [PD activities] as something different*” (P5).

By making the events slightly strange, participants were better able to grasp the difference between PD and their “normal” calendar, while using the same technology. However, this still might have been too subtle for some participants and future work should explore additional strategies.

Theme 3: Being overwhelmed by the large number of additional activities

Conceptually, we chose to overlay the existing calendars with the self-selected, wellbeing oriented activities. This overlay was meant to induce friction, a certain tension between how time use is, and how it could or should be. Of course, an average of 8.4 additional fixed activities per day can be quite overwhelming and invasive.

In fact, feeling overwhelmed was a common theme. P1 said: “*I felt stressed out the first two days, because of all the events in my calendar [...] I thought: ‘Oh wow, I can’t manage this’*” (P1). P2 explained: “*The first thought crossing my mind was: Goodbye to that, you can’t use that anyway*” (P2). She filled her perfect day with activities she would like to do, but confronted with it, it dawned upon her that she still “*had to work [...] super unrealistic [...] I had only four to five hours left for work*” (P2). P3 was overwhelmed as well, but immediately understood the denseness of his calendar as an “*impulse for certain things [changes]*” (P3). P5 did not feel overwhelmed, since he knew that “*everything that is yellow [the PD activities] has a low priority anyway, to be honest. But it is a hoped-for reminder [...]*” (P5).

Theme 4: Playing with time

The friction induced by superimposing real days with perfect days can only be productive if participants resolve the tension, that is, start to actually “work” or “experiment” with their schedule. P1 started to approach her calendar a little more “creatively” after a while. She now “juggled” and tried for a fresh start by reconsidering each activity: “*[...] because of the calendar, I discovered that it is better for me not to exercise midday, but rather in the afternoon or early evening*” (P1). Likewise, P2 consciously adapted PD to her needs: “*And then I restructured the calendar a little, some events got shortened and then I used it*” (P2). She also coped with the pressure by re-framing her notion of the private activities: “*It became totally easy, because I just cancelled [deleted] events, I could not fit in in a day. Tomorrow is just another day*” (P2). She lowered her expectations and simply tried to fit in as much private activities as feasible. In fact, while PD uses the same element (i.e., an event) as the work calendar, activities (i.e., appointments) are better seen

as suggestions. They could be treated a little more generously: “[...] priority was not so high that I had to slavishly obey. I took a look, acknowledged the suggestion, and tried my best” (P5). This is basically what participants discovered: to take their free time seriously, but not being too strict with themselves. To work with their schedule every day, rather than to blindly submit themselves to it.

Theme 5: Day or week?

A concrete problem that emerged already in the first interview was the unit (here: days) we chose. People have different notions of a perfect day for different days of the week. P3 said that he is not planning the “perfect day, but [...] his week” (P3). In fact, a number of participants insisted on defining two or three perfect days. At the heart of this is their desire to actually spend a day as closely to the ideal as possible. However, without further differentiation this seems impossible. Most activities have “rhythms”. For example, P1 put “seeing friends” in her PD, but later said that it is of course unrealistic to go out every night. A week as a unit seems to stand a better chance to serve as a realistic blueprint compared to a day.

Theme 6: Irritation, sensitization, and internalization

Only three out of the five participants, P1, P2, P5, explicitly reflected on different phases in their relationship to PD. In general, using PD started out negatively (see Theme 3). P1 felt “irritated” in the first two days. P5 tried to “ignore” PD in the beginning. P2 was a little more positive by pointing out that the first week required “working with the calendar, in the sense of experimenting with what fits when” (P2) (see Theme 4). P2 further said: “I tried to carefully avoid irritation, which worked out and there were many days I deleted a lot and I moved around events” (P2).

This “working with time” led to sensitization. P5 explained: “I have a sensitization, I feel it. It can’t express it in numbers, but I intensely thought about, how to actually spend my free time” (P5) and further: “The calendar made me aware of certain elements in my daily routines” (P5). P1 feels more “well-arranged.”

Finally, participants reported a certain internalisation. P1 said: “In the third week, I haven’t thought much about it [the perfect day activities], but moved, deleted, tried to make it happen [...] it was already in my head, somehow” (P1). P2 explained: “At the beginning, I spent more time looking at the calendar. I needed it. [...] in the last week, it was like I already knew all the things important to me, such as writing songs. I did not need to look at the calendar. It was already in my head. I learned: ‘Hey, it is supercool, I can use breaks throughout the day to write a song’” (P2).

Theme 7: What is in a day?

Of course, change differed from participant to participant in terms of content. P1 said that she “still engaged in more or less the same activities, but on different times” (P1). Since she worked from home and mixed private (especially exercise) with work activities throughout the day, her perceived major problem had been “disrupted” days. PD helped with the transition

from work to free time: “[When MPD showed the first private event] I said to myself: ‘Okay, this had been eight or nine hours, now I stop, and just have a look what the calendar offers’” (P1). She also worked late less often, because “we [she and her partner] had to go out [laughs]” (P1) the calendar told her so. In addition, she felt as if she used “the free time [...] really for the activities, I’ve put in [PD]. I don’t hang about and ask myself: ‘What are you actually doing right now?’” (P1). PD helped P1 to establish a better separation between work and private time (both at home) and to be more conscious about the activities, she cares about.

For P2 it was all about establishing rhythms and routines. For example, she defined a morning meditation as an element of her perfect day, an activity she rarely got around to do. Prompted by PD she said to herself: “Okay! I need to set the alarm, to get up, and to just do it. [...] I found it really great and pulled through. [...] a great example of how to build a habit” (P2). For another precious activity, namely writing music, being prompted by and working with PD helped her to identify breaks throughout the day to fit it in: “It [PD] helped me to play music more often” (P2).

Although cautious about the changes instilled by PD, P3 was able to identify two concrete situations. Similarly to P1, PD helped him with the transition from work to private time: “What was good, was the event which prompted me to wrap-up work, to have a last look at the to-do list and to call it a day” (P3). Another transition was going to sleep: “[...] in the evening, ‘It’s time for bed’ at least it was a reminder to wrest myself free [of whatever I was doing] to get seven hours of sleep” (P3).

P5 explained that there are many obstacles in realizing a perfect day. He engaged in the suggested activities only if there hadn’t been “catastrophes at home” or other “duties.” He pointed out that PD cannot actually remove obstacles, but supports him by reminding “that I actually wanted to do something different” (P5). In fact, PD helped him: “Yes, I even exercised. Maybe not the sports I wanted to do, but at least some sports” (P5). The most important suggested activity (“100% super”) was putting the children to bed.

Theme 8: Scaffolding for a more well-being oriented use of time

P1, P2, P3 and P5 reflected about whether they would be willing to continue using PD or not. P1 would like to use PD further, but mainly because it removes choice: “To let [PD] decide [...] If it is in the calendar, I do not need to make a choice” (P1). P5 just plans to keep important private activities in the work calendar, such as putting the children to bed. For P2 and P3 it was more about keeping up newly established practices. P2 was curious about the future, since she did not plan “to put anything [private] into the calendar.” She stated: “[I] hope that my new routines are so strong already that I just do it” (P2). However, if she felt like “relapsing,” she “would put it [important activities] back into the calendar” (P2). To prevent

relapse may also be the reason for P5 to keep important PD activities in the calendar. P3 plans to further engage in subtle rearrangements of his schedule. He mentions the transition from work to free time in the afternoon, and concentrating work a little more in the morning to have more free time. Similar to P2, he worries about his ability to maintain his newly acquired routines and would use PD in the case of relapse: “[PD] relates to one’s ‘weaker self,’ which is made conscious and which needs to be eliminated [laughs]” (P2). In this sense, PD is understood by the participants as “scaffolding technology” (e.g., Fritz, Huang, Murphy, & Zimmermann, 2014). It provides insight, structure, and motivation for those who feel incapable of implementing their intentions.

Summary and conclusion

For most of our participants the benevolent calendar was a worthwhile, wellbeing-enhancing experience (Theme 1). It prompted rethinking personal time use and promoted the integration of wellbeing-oriented activities into everyday life (Theme 6, 7). Participants reported sensitization towards personal time use and a certain internalization (Theme 6). Already at the end of the three week period, the perfect day calendar became a “scaffolding technology” – a means to prevent relapsing into old habits (Theme 8).

Of course, our findings are limited since they mostly reflect how participants subjectively experienced the perfect day calendar. While an average of 5.2 realized wellbeing-oriented activities per day seems promising, this number is not easy to interpret, since we neither had a control group in the study nor individual baseline measurements. In other words, we neither know how many wellbeing-oriented activities per day are normal nor how many activities each of our participants had before they used the calendar. The change over time within the three weeks was rather mixed. While two participants increased their number of wellbeing-oriented activities over time, for two no change was apparent, and one even decreased the number. Future studies will create a more complete picture. Nevertheless, at least the study shows, that “productivity tools” can play the role of a Trojan horse in wellbeing-oriented design.

From our point of view, *Perfect Days* is already a viable conceptual design. Thought of as a product-service-system, a “wellbeing coach” could explore time use with an individual in a “counselling interview”. In dialogue with the participant, the coach could construct a perfect week (see Theme 5). To lower irritation (Theme 6), only a fixed number of wellbeing-oriented activities (e.g., 4) should be allowed – at least in the beginning (Theme 3). The friction created by the superimposed activities needs to be apparent, but bearable. The coach can now prepare a “calendar extension” and ask the participant to import it into her or his calendar, similar to what we did. The activities themselves should be clearly distinguishable from typical work entries (Theme 2), yet occupy the same space to create bearable irritation and then sensitization. A fruitful strategy to distinguish wellbeing-oriented activities from work activities was humour and a little irony. Most participants found the

slightly strange labelling of the wellbeing-oriented activities “charming”. In general, we assume that humour and irony can make necessary friction more bearable (Hassenzahl & Laschke, 2015). Another important aspect is being understanding (Hassenzahl & Laschke, 2015). In the present case, this could be achieved by framing the activities as suggestions rather than fixed appointments and by stimulating people to play around with the activities and to gradually adapt their perfect week to their individual interests and abilities (Theme 7). Of course, the conceptual knowledge gained through the present case can also be used to create a more self-contained version of our benevolent calendar, where, for example, the conversation with a coach is replaced by a prompted self-analysis. In this respect, *Perfect Days* is a conceptual design inviting many different concrete materialisations.

All in all, the present study shows that a mere “productivity tool”, such as a digital calendar, can be transformed into a caring technology, which is just – as one of our participants expressed it – “there and nicely says ‘That’s enough now!’”. This, however, requires explicit rethinking of our all too ubiquitous, innocent, and supposedly “useful” tools in terms of the impact they currently have and could have on psychological wellbeing.

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The temporality of user experience; exploring past and future in two car case studies

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Abstract The importance of understanding the temporal aspects of user experience (UX) has been recognized by the research community as well as by industry. Two studies of cars were performed to further investigate the temporality of user experience. In total 27 drivers participated in the studies; one study was *retrospective* investigating past experiences of cars, and one was *prospective*, researching expectations on future autonomous cars. A mix of qualitative methods was employed, encouraging the participants' reflections through mediation by creative elements. Overlapping themes in the studies were found, and a tentative model was developed based on a temporal sequence in terms of *Aquaintancing*, *Using* and *Transforming*. By breaking down the temporality of user experience into sequences and defining the aspects of UX characterizing each sequence, it is suggested that designers and researchers can be helped in understanding and approaching experiences at these different stages.

Keywords *User experience, Automotive design, User study methodology, Temporality, Autonomous cars*

Introduction

Summarized under the term "User Experience" (UX), researchers as well as industry have over the last couple of decades struggled with understanding more about users' emotional responses to and experience of and with products. This is true also for the car industry. Examples of vehicle UX research include the experience of specific in-car systems such as infotainment touch interfaces (Pitts, Skrypchuk, Attridge, & Williams, 2014), haptic interfaces (Väänänen-Vainio-Mattila et al., 2014) and head-up displays (Soro et al, 2014). The studies mainly address momentary experiences of these systems, i.e. they capture users' direct responses to interacting with the systems and their user interfaces. However, user experience is something that develops and changes over time (see for example Bødker & Klokmoose, 2012; Karapanos et al, 2009; Kujala et al., 2011). Nevertheless, studies investigating vehicle *long-term* user experiences are, to the authors' knowledge, considerably more scarce with few exceptions including a study on adaptive cruise control systems (Eckoldt, Knobel, Hassenzahl, & Schumann, 2012), and a study on parking assistant systems (Trösterer, Wurhofer, Rödel, & Tscheligi, 2014). In addition to lacking a long-term perspective, prospective insights are missing even though they are essential for providing information at early stages of design processes. There is thus a need to further investigate the temporal dimensions of user experience, also for the automotive industry.

User experience and temporality

User experience frameworks

Today, a number of different approaches exists which addresses the issue of emotions and experience. With

an emphasis on affect and emotional response, a basic model of product emotions was put forward by Desmet (2002). According to the model an emotion is the result of an appraisal process where the characteristics of the product are appraised against the concerns of the individual. When the characteristics of a product match the concerns of a user, positive emotions are elicited. When there is a mismatch, on the other hand, negative emotions are elicited.

Norman (2004) chose to describe three levels of emotion design; 'visceral design' referring to a product's appearance and appeal to the user's senses, 'behavioural design' related to, for instance ease-of-use, and 'reflective design', i.e. how the product appeals to the user's self-image, personal satisfaction and meaning over time.

Developing on the concept of experience, Hekkert and Desmet (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007) defined product experience as "the entire set of affects that is elicited by the interaction between a user and a product, including the degree to which all our senses are gratified (aesthetic experience), the meanings we attach to the product (experience of meaning) and the feelings and emotions that are elicited (emotional experience)" (Hekkert, 2006, p.160).

Focusing on interaction and use, Hassenzahl et al. (2008) described user experience as constituted along two product dimensions; pragmatic and hedonic qualities. Pragmatic qualities of a product concern the "do-goals" of a product, i.e. practical goals of interaction such as making phone calls or uploading documents on a web site. The other category of goals, the "be-goals" of a product, concerns the hedonic

qualities, i.e. how the design enables human needs beyond the instrumental, such as “being close to another person” or “being competent at work”. Be-goals thus move the concept of user experience beyond purely task-related goals for product use.

User experience and temporality

Even though time may be an implicit dimension in the frameworks described earlier, they do not *specifically* address temporality, i.e. how user experience is evolving over time, acknowledging the transitions between anticipated use, momentary use and use over extended periods of time. The relevance of temporality in UX studies has been shown by Bødker and Klokmoose (2012) who, based on an interview study with iPhone users, described users as transitioning between excited states, stable states and unsatisfactory states. Another example is Karapanos et al. (2009) who described iPhone users’ temporal user experience in terms of *orientation, incorporation and identification*. The orientation phase refers to users’ initial experiences where they are excited or frustrated when encountering new functionality. In the incorporation phase, the product becomes meaningful in the users’ daily life, where usability and usefulness are important factors. Finally, in the identification phase, the product is connected to the users’ self-identity. Additional temporal UX research has investigated how hedonic and pragmatic factors (cf. e.g. Hassenzahl et al. 2008) interplay with the user experience, indicating that pragmatic factors (e.g. usability) is predominant for user experience judgments at initial stages of use, whereas hedonic values (e.g. aesthetic, stimulation) became more dominant over time (Kujala et al., 2011).

Related to the question of UX temporality is methodology. Even though temporality is a key factor in users’ experiences of and with products, the primary source of knowledge for evaluating UX is assessments of affective responses to products (e.g. by tools such as SAM and PrEmo) and/or experiences of short-term use (for an overview, see Bargas-Avila & Hornbæk, 2011). This issue has been addressed by developing retrospective methodologies, i.e. tracing back usage over time, such as the UX Curve method (Kujala, Roto, Väänänen-Vainio-Mattila, Karapanos, & Sinnelä, 2011), the iScale (Karapanos, Martens, & Hassenzahl, 2012) and employing “temporal anchors” (Huang & Stolterman, 2014). The common feature of the mentioned methodologies is that they intend to entice users to describe their ‘journey of use’ in retrospect.

Prospective insights

Another methodological issue from a temporal perspective is the lack of prospective insights from UX studies. Insights for understanding disruptive innovations, i.e. designs that create new values and by this may disrupt the market, can be difficult to elicit from retrospective and momentary methods. As design involves enabling novel experiences, it would be beneficial if research was able provide information also in early stages of design processes, and on products where there are no predecessors. In the automotive area, an example of this type of product is

autonomous cars. Most premium car brands are in the process of prototyping autonomous cars, but none are as yet available for the general public.

One aspect of the prospective is *expectations* on future experiences. Expectations have been found to shape the later outcomes of experiences (see for example Karapanos et al., 2009; Trösterer, Wurhofer, Rödel, & Tscheligi, 2014) and are a recognized part of experience temporality (see for example McCarthy & Wright, 2010). Expectations are based on earlier experiences as well as the user profile and anticipated emotions (Yogasara & Popovic, 2011). In addition to retrospective studies, expectations therefore pose an interesting study case for temporal user experiences, and in the study the subject of experience is thus approached from two perspectives; retrospective and prospective.

Aim and approach

With the overall aim to gain further knowledge of UX temporality, this paper describes two case studies of temporal in-vehicle user experiences, the first with the overall purpose of understanding *past* experiences, and the second addressing expectations on *future* user experiences. Questions posed are: How are the users’ stories of past and future use constituted? Do the stories differ depending upon the retrospective or the prospective timeline? Are there common themes to learn from in the two perspectives?

The first study was *retrospective*, i.e. looking back at cumulative UX, over prolonged use of in-car systems, in this case between 3 months and 3 years (a more detailed description of the study can be found in Pettersson & Karlsson 2015). The second study was *prospective*, i.e. researching the expectations of future user experiences of autonomous cars (a more detailed description of the study can be found in Pettersson 2016). Both studies contained creative elements to stimulate rich reflection as it has been suggested that information is accessible in layers (Karlsson, 1996; Visser et al., 2005) and in order to reach the lower, more inaccessible, levels, ‘*mediating tools*’, such as product representations, cultural probes, photos, drawings, etc., can be employed (Brandt & Grunnet, 2000; Karlsson, 1996; Sanders et al., 2010). The outcome of the two studies were analysed and compared in order to identify common experience aspects and if these aspects had a temporal dimension.

Study 1

Method

The first study employed three methods for retrospective data collection from altogether 16 Swedish drivers. The methods were Contextual Interviews (Beyer & Holtzblatt, 1997), the UX Curve Method (Kujala et al., 2011), and Reflexive Photography (Harrington & Lindy, 1998), aimed to stimulate in-depth reflection by the introduction of creative elements and the situated context in the car.

Prior to the interviews, the participants were asked to take photographs that depicted experiences of

Figure 1. Example of a participant's photo (Participant 4), connected to experiences of relatedness during phone calls in the car, as well as the ease of use of the call list.

significant importance for them. Figure 1 provides one of the participant's photos, as an example.

The photographs were brought to the interview session, where the first part of the study took place in the participant's home or office. Questions regarding experiences over time were posed, and in accordance with the UX curve methodology the participants were asked to draw their experiences over time on a positive/negative and longitudinal scale, as well as mark out memorable experiences. The next part of the interviews took place in the participants' cars, so that the participants could show/act out any experiences important to them in the car. All interviews were recorded, transcribed in full and the content was analysed applying a qualitative data analysis (as described by, for instance Denzin and Lincoln (1998)) together with the UX curves notes and the photographs.

Findings

The participants' user experiences clearly evolved over time as the cars were explored and incorporated into daily life. Three user groups emerged in terms of the overall user experience trends.

- A minor part of the participants (N=3) had a very informed expectations and the overall experience remained stable over time; "...Since I was quite aware of what I'd bought and they (the car brand) delivered what I expected, it (the UX Curve) is quite a straight line." (P4).
- For the largest group of participants (N=9) their experiences exceeded expectations, where positive behaviours and emotions evolved over time.
- The third group (N=4), was increasingly disappointed over time. In this case mainly usability issues lowered the experience ratings after initial high expectation for functionalities.

Expectations for the systems were formative for the initial experiences of use. Most changes were noted in the first half of the UX curves, as the users were exploring the cars, finding shortages as well as benefits through active use. An example of a curve with early experiences is presented in Figure 2. The thrill associated with discovery and stimulation was apparent, all participants enjoyed learning more about using their new cars over time. A typical comment was: "When you get used to it (an in-vehicle system), you look for the next thing" (P3).

Figure 2. Example of a User Experience Curve (P7), with several initial experiences.

Three principal aspects were found to be formative for the long-term user experience of in-vehicle systems:

- *Influence of other products.* All participants had in-vehicle systems that were connected to smart phones, and expectations were transferred from the phones to the car; "You can't update and if you don't like it (the in-car GPS) you have paid a lot of money and you're stuck with it." (P4). The users also continuously compared the car to other technology in their life, such as computers.
- *Influence of new behaviours.* Secondly, new behaviours emerged over prolonged use and these new behaviours altered the experience considerably over time. Examples of such established behaviours and routines were the use of hands-free phone, using apps for monitoring the car from home and working in the car; "It is a nice feeling with modern technology that you feel you are in the office but you are still transporting yourself. I think it is a good feeling and you feel that you are effective and solving many things at once. I did it yesterday" (P 6). These established habits were formative to the UX over time.
- *Influence of social settings.* Thirdly, many experience stories concerned social aspects of using in-vehicle systems and social routines such as calling family members on the way home became important routines in the users' lives. Technology in the car was also often found to serve as an enabler for joint experiences, for example enjoying podcasts or audio books together with family members in the car, or using the car to simplify everyday social life; "When the children get tired in the car, and you can have them borrow your phone and pick songs on Spotify (to play through the car's infotainment system), they like that because they have the feeling that they control something" (P14).

Method

In the second study, 11 Los Angeles drivers took part. The study made use of the "Setting The Stage for Future Automotive Experiences" method (Pettersson, 2014), developed to support user reflections on temporal experiential dimensions of expectations. The participants were asked to sit inside a "car" outlined on the floor in a room (Figure 3). They were first asked about their current daily commutes, anchoring any stories in the participants' personal perspectives. They

Figure 3. The Stage before, during and after study 2.

were then encouraged to imagine and enact a routine drive in an autonomous car, engaging both body and mind in reflections of expectations on different stages of usage; i.e. initial use and long-term routines. The placement in the “car” was intended to offer contextualization of the on-road, in-car context, allowing actions to be enacted as they would be performed in a real car. In addition, questions were posed concerning topics such as expected value, emotional responses and attraction, and how these would change over time. The participants were also asked to rearrange/remove seats and make drawings of any desired design changes.

The sessions were video- and audio-recorded and the audio-recording transcribed in full. As in Study 1, a qualitative content analysis was carried out (cf. Denzin & Lincoln, 1998) combined with Visser et al’s description of analysing generative methods for user studies (Visser et al., 2005).

Findings

The participants had high expectations for a smarter, efficient and relaxed life in the autonomous cars: “I would think like “wow I could be like, so amazingly efficient” (in an autonomous car). I could actually get in the car and get this done while the car is taking me to this destination, and then I could get that done too, and then do something else” (P1). Before actually daring to use the technology, they expected to make acquaintance with autonomous car through media, social connections, on the road and in showrooms. This phase was experienced as formative to later decision to trust the technology, and it was apparent that expectations were not formed in isolation but were heavily influenced by social and media influence; “(Trust) would depend on the vehicle manufacturer’s reputation and people I know in my social circle who may have experienced the technology.” (P24).

Attraction was expected to arise also from favourable aesthetics and novelty found in the interior of the car; “I think it would just be a new a canvas. I think you would have to lose all the regular car interior things, that we all know and use” (P20).

The participants all expected to eventually become engaged in using autonomous cars, although some more than others thought it would take time to gain trust. In expectations for active use, the participants related to previous use of other technology (e.g. semi-autonomous systems in current cars, smart phones and other domestic products), ease-of-use and stimulation. This included clear feedback and intuitive handling, but also the freedom of not having to control

functionality (unless specifically requested by the user); “Yeah, you can’t be involved (in traditional driving information) because you are completely immersed in another thought (when no longer engaged in driving the car). That’s not what that’s (the autonomous car) supposed to be. /.../ It has to be a new thing”. (P27)

In addition to the expectations on active use, autonomous cars were expected to make a tangible difference in the user’s life. This could for example be in form of introducing valuable new habits and routines during the daily commute, even having an effect on where to live; “Every place you go here is a distance so it would be a relief not to have to be “on” all the time. By the end of the day I’m often exhausted, a self-driving car would help me still do things. I don’t live in the heart of LA, so I have to drive a lot to do business and I can get sick of it. (...) I think it (an autonomous car) would change my evening routine, since I wouldn’t be as drained after a day of driving”. (P21). The meaning of the car was expected to transform, from today’s situation where control is extremely important, to being able to completely immersed in selected other activities, while being transported. The car was expected to create an augmented bridge between work and home life, bringing relief from unwanted emotions; “The car has no emotion and reacts exactly as it has to, while you as a passenger avoided that set of emotions. /.../ Once I trust the car, many things that I think would make me anxious would no longer make me anxious. /.../ All the emotions and feelings that surround (LA traffic), that create the mood and transition from drive to home and make you upset with your kids, your wife, your dog, and so on. Now you have a smile. Less anger is transferred from the road to home (with an autonomous car).” (P19)

Cross-case analysis

The two studies investigated users’ past experiences of in-car systems (Study 1) and expected future experiences of and with an autonomous car (Study 2). Even so, overlapping themes were found, such as information of what made/would make the participants *attracted* to the car, how they experience/would experience *use* and how they had seen/expected to see their habits and relation to the car and its systems *transform* over time. Based on the narratives, these themes could be arranged in a temporal sequence. The sequence can be described as *Aquaintancing, Using and Transforming* (Figure 4.). Rejection took place when users had not been/was expected not to be attractive enough during *Aquaintancing*, or had/would lead to an unsatisfactory use situation, or unable to establish acquire habits and value of use over time. In accordance to this, the model highlights the process of user experience; transition from one stage to another is reached if the previous stage is satisfying.

In the narratives certain ascribed product features were emphasized in the different stages but also other things than the cars’ attributes influenced the experiences, such as social relations, expectations regarding other products, earlier interactions and

Figure 4. The tentative model of User Experience Temporality describing the “acquaintancing”, “using” and “transforming” sequences.

established routines connected to the car and daily habits. The factors are summarised in Table 1, and are not to be seen as set and stable, but give direction to the factors that foremost characterized each stage, as found in the two studies.

The first sequence, *Acquaintancing*, defines the stage where the user got/get to know the car before actual use. In both studies, a number of aspects were found to be influential, such as perceived novelty, aesthetics and functionality. A more complex interdependency was found to influence the ‘want’ for a new car than what Norman (2004) refers to as visceral aspects. In both studies it was also observed how acquaintancing was heavily influenced by social factors, such as friends talking about the technology in the car, interacting with salesmen or reading about it in social media. The acquaintancing phase set the expectations for later UX. In Study 1 the expectations influenced the outcomes of later experiences; in Study 2 this phase consisted of vividly imagining the future use where the expectations contained both “be-goals” and “do-goals” (cf. Hassenzahl et al., 2008). If the car was/will be found attractive enough to make the user trust and want the car, this “want” was/would be the lever that would enable actual use.

The second sequence, *Using* the car in an everyday life context contained elements such as ease-of-use (cf. Norman, 2004; Hassenzahl et al. 2008) and stimulation (cf. Hassenzahl et al., 2008) but also building trust in the car by interacting with it and its systems. An important aspect is that this sequence in itself contained temporal dimensions, i.e. stimulation and trust had/were expected to evolve over time, something which is overlooked in most user experience studies (Bargas-Avila & Hornbæk, 2011). In Study 1 stimulation represented encountering new and sometimes unexpected features over time, such as updateable interfaces offering continuous stimulation. In Study 2 stimulation signified the initial confirmation of the novelty of the autonomous car, but also (over time) liberating the user to be entertained by

non-car related activities. In both studies, trust referred to predictable, transparent and reliable functionality but in Study 2 trust was further highlighted as a precondition for use, and was expected to grow over time. A use situation where these aspects were satisfactory was/would be the next lever into the next experience sequence.

The final sequence of *Transforming* describes how the car made/will make a long-term difference to the user, by new behaviours and assigned meaning of the car. This sequence encompasses the aspects of user experiences that are foremost established over prolonged use, i.e. identification, meaning and attachment, also present in the frameworks by Norman (2004) and Hassenzahl et al. (2008). However, this is also the sequence where the car transformed/was expected to transform everyday life. In Study 1, this was exemplified by the changes in work, leisure and social routines that the in-car technology offered. In Study 2, the autonomous car held far reaching expected possibilities of a less stressed and more efficient life in and with cars, even expected to influence where to live and work. These user experience aspects move well beyond sensory and interaction dimensions, i.e. from a micro-level on which the user experience the product through her senses, and cognitive and emotion responses to interaction, into a “macro-level” where the product plays a part in transforming the users’ activities and choices. This macro-level can be compared Forlizzi’s (2008) framework of Product Ecology where a web of social activities, life choices and practices are influenced by the artefact.

Discussion

The temporal model of user experience presented in this paper bears resemblance with the frameworks and models described earlier (cf. Norman, 2004 and Hassenzahl et al., 2008). However, the model emphasises the *temporal* aspects, including expectations as highlighted also by, for instance Olsson, Lagerstam, Kärkkäinen, and Väänänen-Vainio-

Table 1. User experience sequences.

	Acquaintancing	Active Use	Transformation
Aspects of UX	Aesthetics	Ease of use	Habits
	Functionality	Stimulation	Routines
	Novelty	Social influences	Attachment
	Social influences	Reability	Meaning(fullness)
	Trust building	Previous experiences of similar products	Self-identification
	...	Trust	...
		...	

Mattila (2011) and Yogasara and Popovic (2011). Furthermore, even though similarities exist in terms of addressing goal fulfilment, the last stage, *transforming*, is not incorporated in the models and frameworks mentioned. This last sequence in the model highlights the importance of new habits that are formed around products, and how the meaning (fullness) of the product may change over time, contributing to the overall user experience. What Hassenzahl et al. (2008) describe as “be-goals” of a product are thus not to be seen as set and stable. In the studies reported here they were rather found/were expected to transform. There is thus a dialectic relationship between product and user, extending beyond the direct experiences of product-user interactions. For example, the technology offered by a car may come to influence daily practices such as social routines or even more fundamental choices, such as where to live. It is possible that this expansion may not be relevant for less complex products but for the users involved in the studies, these experience aspects were essential and integrated parts of the overall user experience. The results highlight that as it is not possible to give an informed evaluation of a complex product, such as a car, from momentary instances of use. However, experience studies that do not address user experience over time are predominant (Bargas-Avila & Hornbæk, 2011). In addition, based on the findings from Study 1, it does not appear feasible to filter out other products and people from research of user experience. Still, user experience studies commonly address only one user and one product. There is thus a need for a methodology that can provide further understanding of the longitudinal and “ecological” aspects of a product. Furthermore, the taxonomy of user experience could favourably be expanded; from a focus on direct interactions to also encompassing the “macro-perspective” of introducing new experiences that lead to evolved habits and routines that appear important in users’ lives. The model presented in this paper offers one suggestion of such an expansion of the user experience terminology.

The proposed model is based on two studies and further research is needed to confirm the relevance of the sequence as well as to develop on the aspects to consider in each phase. The first study describes how behaviours and experiences change over time, suggesting that there are limitations to what can be understood at one instance in time. This is evidently also true for prospective scenarios; there is not one, stable version of future experience. Nevertheless, as designers need to suggest versions of the future experiences, doing so with an informed user perspective is desirable. The tentative model can help researchers as well as designers to reflect on what aspects of user experience that can be accessible at what point in time of development. By breaking down the temporality of user experience into a sequence, designers and researchers can be enabled in understanding and approaching experiences at different stages. For example, with a novel product as an autonomous car, the interfaces must be designed to cater for the need of initial stimulation and novelty, as well as being allowed to fade into the background as

alternative activities and priorities emerge. The segmentation of the model could also aid the understanding of what aspects of user experiences one can address at what stage of evaluation. Furthermore, it highlights the need to design also for the development of habits and routines, as they become very important in the use and the experience of the product. As pointed out by for example Trösterer et al. (2014), habits evolving around *social behaviour* appear have a strong influence on user experiences. As time pass, the interface itself fades to the background and the activities it enables are the center of attention.

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Hot spots or havens? Aligning workplace design with personal factors to enhance wellbeing

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Abstract Aligning work tasks, workspace design and personal factors such as personality and national culture can lead to the development of workplaces where mood, worker performance, and wellbeing are optimized. In these spaces, workers' preferences and expectations of where they will do a good job are consistent with environments provided. The purpose of the current study was to learn more about links between personality, national culture, experiences with workplace design, and perceptions of which work environments support working well. Extraverts select to do solo work requiring concentration in more communal environments than introverts and also seem more concerned about the comfort of visitors to their workstation than introverts. Extraverts also felt that they would do their current job well in more visually energizing environments than introverts. People in individualistic cultures feel that for them to do their current job well it was more important that they communicate with other people frequently than people from collectivist cultures. Insights drawn from this project can be used to inform the development of workplace environments that enhance mood, professional performance, and wellbeing.

Keywords *Personality, National culture, Workplace design, Wellbeing, Performance*

Introduction

All the world's a stage, and personal factors influence the sorts of sets on which we should live out our lives.

Personality and national culture are personal factors that have been linked conceptually to the experience of design, but little rigorous research has probed specific features of physical workplaces that support various personalities and cultures. Generally, design that recognizes and reflects personal factors enhances user mood and wellbeing (Gifford, 2014) and user wellbeing is an important component of positive design (Desmet and Pohlmeier, 2013).

Mood and workplace design are closely linked (Veitch, 2012). Mood has been tied to how broadly or narrowly a person is thinking (Fredrickson and Branigan, 2005). When people are in an upbeat mood and thinking more broadly, their minds are more likely to work in ways that are consistent with better performance of knowledge work. For example, people thinking more broadly are likely to be better at problem solving (Isen, 2001), innovative and creative thought (Isen, Johnson, Mertz, and Robinson, 1985), getting along with others (Isen, 2001), and even healing, as their immune systems function more effectively (Salovey, Rothman, Detweiler, and Steward, 2000).

Personality has a significant effect on a person's experiences in a particular physical environment (Little, 1987). Theoreticians such as Little have integrated insights drawn from research in

personality, environmental psychology and other social sciences to conclude that aligning personality and design can positively influence mood, performance, and environmental satisfaction at work and elsewhere. The specific forms of the physical environment that support various personality profiles have been sparsely researched, however.

National culture "consists of the unwritten rules of the social game. It is the collective programming of the mind that distinguishes the members of one group or category of people from the others" (Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov, 2010, p. 6). Like personality, national culture has been linked conceptually to optimal design (Zhang, Feick, and Price, 2006), but the specific physical forms that support it have not been thoroughly researched.

This study was initiated to better understand how workplace design can support national culture and personality-based user groups. It also gathered information that more generally should inform workplace design.

Personality concepts

Personality influences experiential responses to a given environment (Little, 1987), as described above. McCrae and Costa define it as "dimensions of individual differences in tendencies to show consistent patterns of thoughts, feelings, and actions" (2003, p. 25).

The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) personality assessment system is “enormously popular [i.e., frequently used in corporate and other settings]. More than 2.5 million people are estimated to take it every year” (Little, 2014, p. 24). Research indicates that contemporary versions of the MBTI are reliable and valid, particularly for the continuous scores that were used for many of the analyses reported here (Gardner and Mantinko, 1996). For example, scores on the MBTI’s extraversion-introversion scale are closely correlated with extraversion-introversion scores obtained using other instruments (Carlson, 1985).

The MBTI categorizes personality using four criteria: preferences for ways of focusing attention (**E**[xtraverted]-**I**[ntroverted]), taking in information (**S**[ensing]-**I**[ntuitive]), making decisions (**T**[hinking]-**F**[eeling]), and dealing with the external world (**J**[udging]-**P**[erceiving]) (Myers, 1998).

There are two preferred ways of focusing attention: extraverted or introverted (abbreviated as E or I). As described by Myers (1998), extraverts “like to focus on the other world of people and activity. They direct their energy and attention outward and receive energy from interacting with people and from taking action” (1998, p. 9). In contrast introverts “like to focus on their own inner world of ideas and experiences. They direct their energy and attention inward and receive energy from reflecting on their thoughts, memories, and feelings” (1998, p. 9).

People who have different preferred ways of taking in information are described, using the MBTI system, as sensing or intuitive, in short, as S or N. As Myers describes, sensing types “like to take in information that is real and tangible. . . [they] are especially attuned to practical realities” (1998, p. 9). Intuitives, in contrast “Like to take in information by seeing the big picture, focusing on the relationships and connections between facts” (Myers, 1998, p. 9). Sensing types are more methodical in their assessments of situations and problems while Intuitives are more likely to trust hunches.

When making decisions, people may have a preference for thinking or feeling. People who prefer thinking “like to look at the logical consequences of a choice or action. . . They are energized by critiquing and analyzing” (Myers, 1998, p. 10). In contrast, people who prefer to use feelings when making decisions “like to consider what is important to them and to others involved. . . Their goal is to create harmony” (Myers, 1998, p. 10).

Dealing with the external world is linked to two preferences, judging and perceiving. People who prefer judging “like to live in a planned, orderly way, seeking to regulate and manage their lives. They want to make decisions, come to closure, and move on. . . they are energized by getting things done” (Myers, 1998, p. 10). In contrast, people who prefer to perceive the external world “like to live in a flexible, spontaneous way, seeking to experience and understand life, rather than control it. . . They are energized by their resourcefulness in adapting to the demands of the

moment” (Myers, 1998, p. 10).

Research published in the peer-reviewed press has not comprehensively evaluated links between the four sets of preferences outlined by the MBTI and specific physical components of supportive workplace environments. A few studies have looked at how environments can support the extraversion-introversion dimension of personality, generally.

Eysenck’s work indicates that extraverts do not process information that they receive through their senses as well as introverts, so a greater amount of environmental stimulation is required for them to achieve the same arousal level as introverts (1967). Extraverts should therefore generally prefer more energizing workplace and other environments than introverts and perform better in those more energizing environments than introverts.

Compared to introverts, extraverts are more likely to choose to spend time in spaces where other people are apt to be, such as hotel lobbies; having other people present makes a space more stimulating (Eddy and Sinnett, 1973). Introverts prefer to stand and sit further from people they’re interacting with than extraverts (Gifford, 1982). This not only leads to larger personal spaces while seated or standing still, but also when walking down hallways.

Extraverts are more likely to choose to work in an open furniture arrangement than introverts, which means that they are less likely to place a piece of furniture, such as a desk or a table, between themselves and a person they are meeting with (McElroy, Morrow, and Ackerman, 1983). Extraverts add more personalizing elements to their workspaces than introverts (Wells and Thelen, 2002).

National culture concepts

Hofstede established a system for categorizing national culture and has updated his framework as new research becomes available (Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov, 2010). It currently describes national cultures using six parameters:

- *Power Distance* – the extent to which members of a society accept the fact that power is not distributed equally among them
- *Individualistic-Collectivistic* – the extent to which ties between people are loose or strong
- *Masculine-Feminine* – the extent to which emotional gender roles are distinct or overlap
- *Uncertainty Avoidance* – “The extent to which the members of a culture feel threatened by ambiguous or unknown situations” (p. 191).
- *Long-Term - Short-Term Orientation* – “Long-term orientation stands for the fostering of virtues oriented toward future rewards. . . short-term orientation, stands for the fostering of virtues related to the past and present—in particular, respect for tradition, preservation of ‘face,’ and fulfilling social obligations” (p. 239).
- *Indulgence-Restraint* – the extent to which people feel free to enjoy life

People from individualistic cultures expect and prize

privacy more than people from more collectivistic cultures (Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov, 2010).

Purpose of this study

The purpose of the current study was to learn more about links between personality, national culture, experiences with workplace design, and perceptions of which work environments support working well. Insights drawn from this project can be used to inform the development of workplace environments that enhance mood, professional performance, and wellbeing (Little, 1987; Veitch, 2012).

Methodology

Source of variables examined in this study

The MBTI was electronically administered to 2272 people in 68 countries, who wished to learn more about their own personalities, over the summer of 2015 by CPP (formerly known as Consulting Psychologists Press). After answering CPP’s demographic and personality questions, people were asked if they were willing to answer questions about workplace design. Those who agreed (n=1815) then responded to a number of workplace design-related questions. Response rates differed, depending on the particular question, but the lowest response rates ranged between 1500 and 1700 respondents/item.

Personality variables of primary focus in this study were four MBTI ‘continuous preference’ scores for EI, SN, TF, and JP. Categorical variables of the four MBTI preferences were also used as grouping variables for some analyses.

Workplace questions

Several workplace related issues were addressed:

- *Participants were asked how important it was for them to communicate with other people frequently, and, separately, to perform work alone that requires a lot of concentration, to do their current jobs well. Five-point Likert response options ranged from not at all important to extremely important.*
- *A set of forced choice questions asked people to “think about the design of the workspace where you believe you could do your current job well.” Respondents indicated if in this space they could see and hear other people or not. They were also asked if in this space they could work alone or with others most of the time.*
- *Additional multiple choice questions asked study participants to describe their current workstation*

and the sort of individual workstation at their employer’s office in which they would do their current job well (answered by picking 5 elements from 22 options).

- *Participants were asked, via a multiple choice question, where they would choose to do solo work that requires a lot of concentration and where they would choose to have scheduled face-to-face meetings with others.*

Results

Respondents

Of 2272 total people taking the MBTI, 1815 (80.5%) agreed to answer additional questions related to workplace design. The full sample of participants was culturally diverse, coming from 6 different global regions. See Table 1.

North America (34.6%) and Africa (39.6%) were most represented in this sample. Of the survey respondents, 54.2% (n=983) were female; 42.6% (n=773) were male.

Importance of communicating with others and solo work

Environment

Participants, who were assigned different sorts of workstations, were asked how important it was (for them to do their current job well) for them to communicate with others frequently, and, separately, to do solo work requiring concentration. Table 2 presents that information.

First, the importance of *communicating* frequently with others was lowest for those in a cubicle with walls too high to see over, when sitting, and for those at a table they didn’t share with others. It was deemed highest by those in a cubicle with walls they could see over, and for those in a private office (walls to ceiling and a door). The importance of *working alone* on work requiring concentration was lowest for those sitting at a table that they don’t share, and highest for those in a cubicle with walls they cannot see over. Finally, it was interesting to find, that for this sample of people, communicating with others was generally considered to be more important than working alone.

Personality

Extraverts were more likely to rate the importance of communication with others highly (r= .24); people who felt that performing work alone was highly important were more likely to be introverts (r= .14). (Note, the negative sign in the first correlation is a function of the type of scaling used for the IE scale.) Both of these relationships were significant at p<.05. Table 3 shows that extraverts’ mean scores were significantly different from introverts for both questions.

Although both groups feel that both activities are important, extraverts were more likely to feel that it is important that they communicate with other people frequently to do their job well than introverts. In contrast, that relationship reverses itself when considering solo work requiring concentration; introverts feel that performing work alone that

Table 1. Survey respondents by global region.

Global Regions	Frequency	Percent
Middle East	204	9.0
Europe	65	2.9
Africa	899	39.6
North America	786	34.6
Asia	203	8.9
India Sri Lanka	115	5.1
Total	2272	100.0

Table 2. Importance of work activity for people in different types of workstations.

Current assigned workstation	Communicate		Work Alone	
	Mean*	N	Mean*	N
A cubicle with walls too high to see over when you are seated	4.5	215	4.0	213
A cubicle with walls that you can see over when you are seated	4.7	280	3.8	281
A seat at a table that you SHARE with others, no dividers (or only a few inches tall) between you and co-workers	4.6	198	3.8	197
A seat at a table that you DON'T share with others where there no dividers of any type between you and co-workers	4.5	105	3.6	104
An office for one person with 4 walls that reach to the ceiling and door that closes	4.7	494	3.8	488
An office with desks for 2 to 4 people with no dividers between the desks, 4 walls, with door	4.6	181	3.9	181
Total	4.6**	1473	3.8**	1464

* One-way anovas were significant at <.05 for both work activities

** Paired samples t-test, significant at <.05

requires concentration is more important than extraverts do. However, both feel that communicating with other people is more important than working alone. There were no differences between these two work activities for any of the other three MBTI categories.

Management level

The importance of communicating with others and doing solo work has generally been found to be related to job level (Brill, Weidemann, and the BOSTI Associates, 2001). Job level comparisons (supervisory vs. non-supervisory respondents) were made to assess the importance of these different work tasks to do one's current job well. Table 4 shows that the importance of communicating with others, and the importance of performing work alone are different for supervisors and non-supervisors.

Supervisors were more likely to feel that communicating with others frequently was more important to doing their job well than was performing work alone. The reverse was true for non-supervisors; they thought that to do their current job well they required more solo work and less communication with others.

Analyses indicated that there was a fairly even split between extraverts (47.3%) and introverts (52.7%) at the entry/non-supervisory level, and again an even split (extraverts=50.1% and introverts=49.9%) at the intermediate management level. However, the situation was different at the executive level; 60.8% of executives were extraverts and 39.2% introverts.

Table 3. Importance of work activity.

To do your job well, how important is it to:	Extraverts (n=863)	Introverts (n=864)
Communicate with other people frequently*	4.8	4.5
Perform work alone that requires a lot of concentration*	3.7	3.9

* p<.05, t-test between independent groups. (Scales: 1=not at all; 5 = very important)

Chosen locations for doing solo work or communicating with others

The previous section provided information about the importance of communicating with others or doing solo focused work. This one will address the choice of location for doing those work activities.

Environment

When asked where they would choose to have face-to-face scheduled meetings, there was general consensus (63.1%), for people in all types of workstations, that they would select 'a room at their employer's office, with floor to floor walls, a ceiling, and a door' and not their assigned workstation. The only exception was for people who already had a private office; they selected their own office 43% of the time and the equivalent type of space (floor to ceiling walls and a door), 45% of the time.

The chosen location for doing solo work requiring concentration showed a similar pattern, although not as strong. The first choice for everyone, except for those in a private office, who selected their own office most (48.8%), was also for 'a room at their employer's office, with floor to floor walls, a ceiling, and a door'. The second most frequent location for doing solo work, for all those in workstations that had little or no enclosure, was for their own workstation. That was reasonable, since they would presumably have their work materials in their own space, regardless of its 'privacy'. The third choice for doing solo work alone was in their home office (24% of the sample).

Table 4. Mean level of importance of work tasks, by job level.

How important is it to:	Non-Supervisory (n=494)	Supervisory (n=864)
Communicate with other frequently*	4.5	4.7
Work alone for 'concentration' tasks*	3.9	3.7

* p<.05, t-test between independent groups. (Scales: 1=not at all; 5 = very important)

Analyses did not reveal any statistically significant differences in the design of current assigned workstations that participants selected as locations for solo work requiring concentration or for scheduled face-to-face meetings and current assigned workstations not selected for the performance of these tasks.

Personality

Personality scores were compared for people who selected different kinds of workstations as their preferred place to do solo work or have scheduled face-to-face meetings. The workstation types they could choose are shown in Table 5.

For those doing work alone that requires concentration, there were differences in places selected to complete these tasks based on extraversion/introversion, sensing/intuition, and judging/perceiving personality preferences. Those choosing to work in a communal space were more extraverted; those choosing to work in a room with floor to ceiling walls, a door, and no others there were more introverted. Those choosing to work in their current assigned space had the strongest sensing score, whereas those choosing a more communal space had the weakest sensing score, one that was almost equivalent to the midpoint of the scale (0). This same pattern was found for judging/perceiving. Those choosing their own workstation had the strongest judging score; those choosing the communal space were exactly at the midpoint (0) of the preference scale.

When asked where they would choose to have scheduled face-to-face meetings with others, the findings were different. Only one of the four types showed a significant difference in this case, and that was for the sensing/intuitive type. All choices fell on the sensing end of the continuum, but the strongest sensing score was for those choosing to have a face to face meeting in a room with floor to ceiling walls, a door, and no others there. The weakest sensing score was for the choice of a communal space for a meeting.

Being in a primary, assigned territory was more likely to be selected by people doing solo work requiring concentration than by people having scheduled face-to-face meetings.

Extraverts were more likely to feel that in a workspace where they could do their current job well they were would be able to see and hear other people while introverts had the reverse opinion ($p < .05$ independent samples t-tests). At the same significance levels, introverts felt that they would do their current job well in a space where they could work alone most of the time, while extraverts feel their performance would be optimized in spaces where they could work with others most of the time.

A related question looked at those who said they could do their job well in a workstation where they could not be seen or heard by their co-worker vs those who selected a workstation where they could see and be heard by their co-workers. An independent samples t-test was done to compare the mean scores on the

Table 5. Personality variables and location choices for different work activities.

WHERE WOULD YOU CHOOSE TO DO SOLO WORK REQUIRING CONCENTRATION?					
Workstation Choices	~N	E-I*	S-N*	T-F	J-P*
In my current individual assigned workstation at my employer	445	-0.016	-0.417	-0.570	-0.575
In a room at my employer's office with floor to ceiling walls/a door/no others there	445	0.103	-0.374	-0.648	-0.495
In a room at my employer's office with floor to ceiling walls/ a door/others doing solo work	143	-0.011	-0.373	-0.476	-0.504
In a communal space at my employer's office, such as a cafeteria	42	-0.249	-0.063	-0.370	0.000
In my home office	380	-0.009	-0.240	-0.540	-0.543
Total	1455	0.016	-0.343	-0.571	-0.518

WHERE WOULD YOU CHOOSE TO HAVE SCHEDULED FACE-TO-FACE MEETINGS W/ OTHERS?					
Workstation Choices	~N	EI	S-N*	T-F	J-P
In my current individual workstation at my employer's office	289	-0.035	-0.309	-0.579	-0.558
In a room at my employer's office with floor to ceiling walls, a door, No others	905	0.061	-0.396	-0.588	-0.541
In a room at my employer's office with floor to ceiling walls, a door, Others doing solo work	70	-0.113	-0.362	-0.492	-0.499
In a communal space at my employer's office, such as a cafeteria	162	-0.116	-0.130	-0.531	-0.368
Total	1426	0.013	-0.346	-0.575	-0.523

* Significant differences between means, 1-way anovas, across workstation types, $p < .05$

Note: Negative scores on the above scales are associated with the first preference letter in the pair.

four MTBI types. Only the extravert/introvert (EI) scale showed a significant difference in personality score for these conditions. Those who selected a workstation where they and co-workers could not be seen and heard had a significantly higher introvert score, than those who chose being seen and heard (they scored on the extravert end of the scale).

As can be seen below, the fifth most frequently chosen workstation feature was for a workstation that had dividers between them and co-workers that impeded sound transmission.

Workstation features where current work could be done well

Most preferred workstation attributes

People were asked what attributes they would select for 'a workstation at your employer's office where you would do your current job well.' There were 22 choices; participants were asked to pick 5 of them. In order of frequency of selection, the top 5 workstation elements selected were:

1. Lots of natural light (n choosing this=1312)
2. Really comfortable chair for me (n=1111)
3. Views of nature through the windows (n=1042)
4. A visually relaxing environment (n=559)
5. Dividers between me and my co-workers, so I can't hear them and they can't hear me (n=422)

Personality

Each of the above highly preferred attributes had a paired choice that was opposite in nature. For example, for the choice of 'views of nature through the windows', there was also a possible choice of 'views of streets or manmade spaces through the window'. To explore the possibility of there being different personality 'types' which would choose one of the pairs, a t-test for independent means was done for the four MTBI preferences. Table 6 shows the preference pairs for which statistically significant personality differences were found.

In terms of extraversion and introversion (EI), the people who preferred a comfortable chair for themselves, a visually relaxing environment, and workstations dividers that kept co-workers from

hearing what they were saying scored more on the introversion end of the scale. The people who chose the opposite of each of those pairs were more on the extraversion end of the scale. These groups, within each pair, were all significantly different from each other.

All people who chose the natural light pair, and the visually relaxing environment scored on the sensing (negative) side of the SN scale. Those who chose less natural light were more strongly classifiable as sensing than those who chose more natural light. However those choosing the visually relaxing environment were more strongly sensing than those choosing the less preferred visually stimulating environment.

There were no differences between the people choosing one of the pairs for either TF (thinking-feeling) or JP (judging-perceiving).

No personality variable differences were found for the preference pair having to do with views of nature or views of streets and manmade features.

National Culture and Design

Whether the national cultures of participant locations was collectivistic or individualistic was determined using information on country scores on this factor provided by Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov (2012).

People in individualistic cultures felt that for them to do their current job well it was more important that they communicate with other people frequently than people from collectivist cultures (means of 4.6, and 4.4, respectively on the 5 point importance scale, $p < .05$, t-test for independent means).

No statistically significant difference was found between individualistic and collectivistic countries on how important it was for participants to do work alone that requires a lot of concentration.

Chi-square tests assessed links between the design of workspaces where participants believed they could do their current jobs well and national culture. No statistically significant differences were found

Table 6. Mean scores*: Personality measures by preferred features.

Rank	Preferred features	E-I	S-N
1	Lots of natural light		-0.306
	Not much natural light		-0.513
2	A really comfortable chair for myself	0.059	
	A really comfortable chair for visitor	-0.192	
3	Views of nature through the windows		
	Views of streets or manmade spaces through the windows		
4	Visually relaxing environment with few patterns, etc.	0.065	-0.333
	Visually stimulating environment with many patterns, etc.	-0.235	-0.179
5	Workstation dividers keep them from hearing what I'm saying	0.244	
	Allow them to hear what I'm saying	-0.079	

*Only statistically significant ($p < .05$) mean scores are shown in the table above.

between people from individualistic and collectivistic countries in terms of whether in these spaces other people could be seen or heard or whether the participant could work alone most of the time or not in these workspaces. These tests may not have been significant because only 7% of participants in this sample were from collectivistic countries.

Discussion

Aligning work tasks, workspace design and personal factors such as personality and national culture can lead to the development of workplaces where mood, worker performance, and wellbeing are optimized (Little, 1987; Veitch, 2012). In these spaces, workers' preferences and expectations of where they will do a good job are consistent with environments provided.

People who participated in this study were generally assigned workstations at their employer's office whose form aligned with the tasks to be performed there; i.e., people doing solo work requiring concentration had some shielding from other employees.

Overall, study participants would choose to have scheduled face-to-face meetings and to do solo work requiring concentration in a more private space with floor to ceiling walls and a door rather than in more open work areas. This desire is consistent with research indicating that the ability to work without distraction, either with others or alone, is most likely in this sort of environment (Veitch, 2012). Work environments provided by employers should support these choices by providing adequately shielded facilities, etc. Workplace design-related research has shown that people are generally good judges, in a macro-sense, of where they are likely to work well; for example, in a space with more or less visual and acoustic shielding (Veitch, 2012). They are unlikely to be able to share the specific details (for example, divider heights) that optimize performance, however.

Personality types did differ in perceptions of work locations where they would do their current jobs well. Extraverts select to do solo work requiring concentration in more communal environments than introverts and also seem more concerned about the comfort of visitors to their workstation than introverts. Extraverts also felt that they would do their current job well in more visually energizing environments than introverts. These findings are consistent with findings reported by Little (1987) and Eysenck (1967). Stronger sensing and judging types were more likely than those scoring lower on these dimensions to select more visually and acoustically shielded workplaces. This is consistent with sensor's and judger's interest in carefully assessing information and having an orderly life, respectively (Myers, 1998).

Although both extraverts and introverts feel that both activities studied are important, extraverts were more likely to feel that it is important that they communicate with other people frequently to do their job well than introverts. In contrast, that relationship reverses itself when considering solo work requiring concentration; introverts feel that performing work

alone that requires concentration is more important than extraverts do. However, both feel that communicating with other people is more important than working alone. Job level also was linked to clear differences in need to work alone or with others.

In addition, people in individualistic cultures felt that for them to do their current job well it was more important that they communicate with other people frequently than people from collectivist cultures did. Just as design can support particular personalities, as described above, it can recognize this relative concern about communication.

In practice, the insights drawn from this study can be used to design workspaces for employee groups, as workers doing similar jobs tend to have consistent personality profiles (Holland, 1996). Facility management policies generally preclude, for reasons of efficiency and cost, developing workstations in which inter-employee shielding is customized for individual workers. Therefore, providing a range of workstations for use by employees as needed for particular tasks, is prudent.

Design can and should provide the sorts of sets on which we all live our best lives, regardless of personal factors.

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Design, emotion and longer-lasting products - Deliver specific insights to designers how to create emotionally durable products

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Abstract In a world smothered in people and products, it must be questioned what all this 'meaningful stuff' is really for, and why does it transform into 'meaningless rubbish' so quickly? We produce 40 tonnes of waste to manufacture one tonne of electronic products. Of that tonne, 98% are discarded within just six months of purchase. Strategies like *emotionally durable design* help us explore the idea of creating a deeper, more sustainable bond between people and their material things; reducing the consumption and waste of resources by increasing the durability of relationships between users and products. This paper argues that emotionally durable design not only helps designers and manufacturers carve deeper pathways to resource efficiency, but also opens up new innovation possibilities for generating greater levels of brand loyalty and perceived value within customers. Using the metaphor of the ocean, this paper reframes products in terms of *depths* and *shallows* of our material experience; taking us from the handful of objects occupying the seldom seen, *hadal zone* of our deeper material world, to the abundance of material goods occupying the surface, or *epipelagic zone*.

Keywords *Emotional durability, Depth, User experience, Sustainability*

Introduction

Never before have we wanted, consumed and wasted so much. In a world smothered in people and products, it must be questioned what – beyond a conventional understanding of functionality – is all this 'meaningful stuff' really for, and why does it transform into 'meaningless rubbish' so quickly? According to the director of London's Design Museum, Deyan Sudjic, we live in a world drowning in objects (Sudjic, 2008); households with a TV set in each room; kitchen cupboards stuffed with waffle makers, blenders and cappuccino whisks, and drawers swollen with a plethora of pocket sized devices powered by batteries, which themselves are products that take several thousand times more energy to make, than they will ever produce.

The volume of waste produced by today's cyclical pattern of short-term desire and disappointment is a major problem, not just in terms of space and where to put it, but, perhaps more notably, for its toxic corruption of the biosphere. Rapidly rising consumption in newly industrialised countries such as China, India and Brazil puts further stress upon reserves of natural resources (Cooper, 2002). This is why the behavioural strategies like *emotionally durable design* (Chapman, 2005; 2015) are so vital in helping us explore the idea of creating a deeper, more sustainable bond between people and their material things. The ultimate aim is to reduce the consumption

and waste of resources by increasing the durability of relationships between consumers and products. After all, the crisis of unsustainability is a crisis of behaviour and perception, not one of energy and materials.

Considering emotional durability at the design stage helps us tackle the challenge of weaning people off their desire for the new, and helps shape new sustainable business models in which longer lasting products have the potential to present robust economic models for creating products, services and brand-loyal customers – driving future sales, upgrade, service and repair (United Nations, 2013). Take, for example, a toaster that lasts about 12 months. If you can extend that use-career to 18 months through emotionally durable design, you have bought about a 50% reduction in waste consumption in all the materials and energy and systems associated with the production and distribution of that product – this is a significant impact (Chapman, 2015).

A spaceship in your bathroom

The vast majority of resources taken out of the ground today become waste within only three months: waste comprising complex cocktails of plastics, metals and other synthetic compounds no longer recognisable to the microbial decomposers that degrade substances back to their basic nutritional building blocks. It may shock you to know that in terms of consumer

electronics – arguably one of the most impactful areas of design activity today – we produce 40 tonnes of waste to manufacture one tonne of products. Of that tonne of products, 98% are discarded within just six months of purchase. In terms of energy and material alone, this sequence of events is less than 1% efficient. Or, to put it another way, our prevailing system of production and consumption is over 99% inefficient. This, of course, is completely unacceptable and begins to explain why – in an ecological sense – we are in the perilous situation we are in. One might assume that, given the huge quantities of precious resources that find their way into our gadgets, we would take a little more care of them, fix them when they break and, indeed, keep them for longer periods of time. However, as we all know, this simply is not the case.

The majority of today's post-consumer waste (the stuff you and I chuck out) is currently disposed of via community recycling centres (ideal) and landfill sites (less ideal), which leak heavy metals and other toxic contaminants over time, such as arsenic, cadmium, copper, lead, manganese and zinc. These toxic elements find their way into soil and groundwater, threatening biodiversity. Landfills are also known to produce large volumes of methane (CH₄), a greenhouse gas and main contributor to climate change. In fact, CH₄ is 25 times more potent per kilo than CO₂. A smaller percentage of waste is burned using vast incinerators that produce ash, laden with toxic elements such as cadmium, lead, mercury, chromium, tin and zinc, while also releasing acidic gases such as sulphur dioxide and nitrous oxides into the atmosphere. Even the much acclaimed recycling of e-waste consumes large quantities of energy, while the chemicals involved during treatment and sorting often find their way back into the ecosystem, causing further damage. Furthermore, the system is not always as efficient and clean as we might assume. Its costly to separate materials that have been soldered onto circuit boards, and this complex form of e-waste – though responsibly sent for recycling by the user, on their way to the mall – ends up getting shipped to a developing country with little or no environmental law, where it is incinerated, and so the crisis worsens.

Precious elements like gold are surprisingly commonplace in electronic products, largely due to their excellent conductive capabilities. In terms of e-waste, there is more gold in a tonne of phones than there is in a tonne of rocks from a gold mine! This mind-boggling idea begins to shift our focus from waste management, to resource management, as the things we discard are materially resource, if only we designed them in a way for this material to be recovered at end-of-life. However, at present, the rock-bound gold is considered more economically viable to extract than its phone-bound counterpart. This kind of waste is a design flaw, if ever there was one. With rising resource costs, and mounting levels of legislation-driven producer responsibility, situations such as these must change.

I'm not just talking about high-tech products like smartphones and tablets here; even fairly low-tech and banal products like electric toothbrushes,

hairdryers and toasters are highly complex when understood from the perspective of their materials and ingredients. Indeed, they're more like likes spaceships! A cheap and disposable child's remote-control tank, for example, contains a thumbnail-sized microchip, within which you will find over two thirds of the elements of the periodic table. And let's not forget, these precious elements don't come out of the ground in clear glass test tubes, ready for use (think of the chemistry set you had when you were a kid). On the contrary, these rare compounds are mined and clawed from the earth, encased in thousands of tonnes of rock and mud. A complex, highly polluting and energy intensive process of extraction and purification follows, within which lurks the majority of our material world's ecological and social destruction. The plethora of electronic products that surround us are infused with a rich cocktail of complex minerals, precious metals and noxious compounds, which to most of us, are completely unseen, lurking just beneath the surface of our material experience.

Products are like icebergs

Products are like icebergs. They are vast, majestic and mysterious things. They are formed in ways that reflect their provenance, their origins. They don't last forever, but some last longer than others. Yet, as we all know, icebergs are potentially deadly too. There is the part you see, above the surface. Then, there is the part you don't see, below the surface, with the submerged part representing 90% of the total ice mass, or thereabouts. The social and ecological impacts of products are kind of similar. The product being the part of the iceberg you see, and the product's associated impact representing the part you don't see; this is by far the greater part, and also the part that is potentially deadly. As any sailor will tell you, the part of an iceberg you need to worry about is not the part you can see, but the greater, submerged parts.

Morton uses the term, *hyperobjects*, to refer to such things that are vastly distributed in time and space, relative to humans (Morton, 2014), and are both seen, and unseen. He tells us that: 'a hyperobject could be a black hole. A hyperobject could be the Lago Agrio oil field in Ecuador, or the Florida Everglades. A hyperobject could be the biosphere, or the Solar System. A hyperobject could be the very long-lasting product of human manufacture, such as Styrofoam or plastic bags, or the sum of all the whirring machinery of capitalism' (p2). These forms of object systems are all around it, yet as designers and users we tend to forget this. We don't look at the screens of our smartphones, for example, and simultaneously imagine complex networks of satellites orbiting our planet, relaying the signals we both emit and receive. Instead, we tend only to see the part of the product that we are engaging with, as opposed to the much broader infrastructure it sits within. Similarly, we don't tap the blue Facebook icon, and imagine an energy-hungry server in California pushing data on our behalf.

This is one of the thornier challenges for product design: to widen the user's field of vision, to encompass the whole object – the *hyperobject* –

including its relational system. Indeed, for product designers grappling with complex issues of *sustainable design* and *design for the circular economy* it is imperative that your field of vision grows as wide as it possibly can if we are to begin tackling this experiential disconnect. The way we relate to and experience our environment defies logic. We clear carbon absorptive forests, to grow methane-producing meat, and smother vast areas of bio diverse wilderness with ecologically inert urban sprawl, riddled with mazes of oil-dependent highways. This *epistemological error* (Bateson, 1972) tells us how the earth is finite, balanced, synergistic and reactive, and yet we design the world as though it were separable, mechanical and lasting. Indeed, human destruction of the natural world is a crisis of behaviour, and not one simply of energy and material alone, as is often assumed (Chapman, 2015); the decisions we make as an industry, the values we share as a society and the dreams we pursue as individuals collectively drive all that we accomplish, while shaping the ecological impact of our development as a species. This ecological crisis concerns how we think, and the institutions that purport to shape and refine the capacity to think (Orr, 2004, p2).

Never satisfied

The notion of a ‘throwaway society’ is nothing new. In fact, it was as early as 1932 when American economist Bernard London first introduced the term, ‘planned obsolescence’ (made popular by Vance Packard in his monograph *The Waste Makers* (1963)) as a means to stimulate spending among the very few that had money at that time. This proposed shift toward an increasingly disposable material world was initially proposed as a solution to dark economic crisis experienced during the Great Depression in the US (c.1929). However, the ecological impacts of this drive toward planned product failure could not have been anticipated or understood in the 1930s. Today, however, we are all too aware of the catastrophe-making character of these practices. As Slade forcefully argues in his book, *Made to Break: Technology and Obsolescence in America*, the concept of disposability was in fact a necessary condition for America’s rejection of tradition and our acceptance of change and impermanence (Slade, 2007). By choosing to support ever-shorter product lives, he argues that we may well be shortening the future of our way of life as well, with perilous implications for the very near future. Just over a century ago, ‘disposability’ referred to small, low cost products such as disposable razors or paper napkins, whereas today it is culturally permissible to throw anything away anything from TV sets and vacuum cleaners to automobiles and an entire fitted bathroom (Chapman, 2013a). Like flotsam and jetsam, the waste generated through this inefficient system coat the surface of our material worlds, obscuring an otherwise rich set of encounters with the inanimate.

So why are we so perpetually dissatisfied with our things, and why is satisfaction such a utopian idea? The motivational drivers underpinning the act of consumption represent a way of being, of interacting with the world. We transfer resources into products

that provide us with existential mirrors, allowing us to view and experience our dreams and desires in real time. These reflections help us to construct an identity that we feel is individual, while also being indicative of our individual aspirations and dreams. In this respect, objects are meaningful in that they illustrate – both to society and the self – our personal life journeys. The process of consumption also appears to possess a quality of avoidance: by continually busying ourselves within a world of goods and services, we cunningly side step sensations of emptiness through sheer distraction – consumption gives us a sense of purpose, and belonging. However, these mirrors cast reflection that is both short lived, and distorted. The products we deploy to both the mirror and project this identity are relatively fixed in time, however.

Much perceived obsolescence is stimulated by this cycle, in which perfectly effective products seem somehow out-dated, and undesirable by the user, simply because they cast an out-dated reflection of who they were, rather than who they now are, or yearn to be. This continual and iterative process is often referred to as *hedonic adaptation* – the observed tendency of humans to quickly return to a relatively stable level of happiness despite major positive or negative events or life changes (Rosenbloom, 2010). Interestingly, *experiential purchases* (like a massage, a study programme or travel) take longer for us to adapt to and tend to hold value from the longer than *material purchases* (like a camera, a car or a jacket). This is because experiential purchases rely more on memory to be processed and understood, whereas material purchases are more tangible and are experienced in real time, and therefore considered less complex and easier to overcome. Of course, products and experiences are not entirely different things that this crude polarisation is helpful in seeing a distinction, which doesn’t believe to some clues around the endurance of meaning and value in the things we consume.

Similarly, the *Diderot effect* (McCracken, 1988) is a social phenomenon that describes the unstable nature of our relationships with products. This theory describes how consumers are drawn to products that are experienced as reflecting their sense of identity. As a result, it is assumed that the products a given person buys will be somehow complementary to one another, as each object has been selected on a similar set of identity-matching criteria. However, as McCracken points out, the introduction of new possessions can disrupt the previously stable collection of complementary products. In other words, the Diderot effect helps explain the process whereby a new purchase creates dissatisfaction with existing possessions, triggering a spiralling pattern of consumption with hugely destructive environmental, psychological and social implications.

Socially approved patterns of behaviour shape the way we interact with the material world. There are a surprising number of such behaviours, or *norms*, which govern the way we value and use goods. Many of these are so inherent that we are unaware of their existence. Norms are cultural products (including

values, customs, and traditions) (Sherif, 1936), which represent individuals' basic knowledge of what others do and think that they should do (Cialdini, 2003). Sociologists describe norms as informal understandings that govern individuals' behaviour in society. It's very normal, for example, that this paper is written in English, and I will bet that this had not occurred to you until just now, when I mentioned it. Norms work in this way; they go unseen until someone draws attention to it, making it noticeable. Electricity works in this way, it's so normal that we only tend to notice it when it fails, flickers or cuts out entirely.

Norms also influence our perception of product lifespans, and how long our possessions ought to last; a toaster should last four years, a kettle five, a smartphone two and so on. None of us ever consciously decided this, but rather, we were socially conditioned to subscribe to these norms. They are massively influential in our decision-making processes relating to when a particular product should be replaced, or, if it breaks whether we fix it, or dump it. Yet, despite their prominence, norms can often be quite ridiculous. For example, replacing a smartphone because of a cracked screen makes no sense, yet many people do this; it's about as ridiculous as replacing an entire car because of a flat tyre. Both are equally repairable, yet one quite common practice, the other unthinkable.

The depths and shallows of material experience

As we dive downwards to the *hadal zone* (the deepest and least explored part of the ocean, where little life exists) we near the depths of our material worlds, in which the objects become increasingly personal, and idiosyncratic. In contrast to the abundant and heavily populated *epipelagic zone*, there are fewer products down here, things move slower and things seem all the more stable. Down here, on-trend fonts make way for handwritten notes; digital screens make way for torn notepaper and logotypes are elbowed aside by images of forgotten friends, lost family and jilted lovers. In the turbulent storms of material experience, these enduring objects serve to anchor us within a more constant identity, and we cling dearly to them.

Of course, we are each connected to several distinct systems of objects, occupying different depths of material experience. These objects may well sit side-by-side on our shelves, but are divided by fathoms, in an experiential sense. To an observer, the things we own and cherish may appear superfluous, banal, and even venal (Schultz et al., 1989) yet we cling to them because they possess significant levels of personal meaning that defines us individually, as separate from society. On describing the depth and power of inanimate objects, Bruce Hood, author of *Super Sense* (2009), undertook an experiment in which he first hands out a black 1930s fountain pen, which he falsely claimed, belonged to Albert Einstein. Everyone in the audience is desperate to hold it, and shows great reverence and awe toward the object, as though part of Einstein's soul somehow resided within it (Hood, 2009). As matter that we must negotiate, products shape our daily experience in ways that

spark particular stories and thoughts, and designers can therefore influence what these thoughts are. As Julia Lohman describes: when communicating through objects the meaning is created through the materiality of the object. The materials become words; the design becomes the syntax. The piece speaks without the detour of language (Williams, 2012).

The level at which *materialism* manifests – arguably the site of human-made ecological destruction – occurs within the dynamic shallows. The *epipelagic zone* (the shallow part of the ocean, in which the majority of marine life can be found) is populated by a dynamic and shifting mass of manufactured products. This constantly shifting assemblage is deployed to reflect our equally dynamic and unstable identities. As our identities evolve and change, so too must the products we deploy to both mirror and project these ephemeral ideas. This form of materialistic value orientation (MVO) involves the belief that it is important to continually pursue the culturally sanctioned goals of attaining, financial success, having nice possessions, having the right image, and having a high status (Kasser, 2004). In this way, *materialism* is defined as 'the importance a consumer attaches to worldly possessions' (Belk, 1984, p291) or 'a set of centrally held beliefs about the importance of possessions in one's life' (Richins & Dawson, 1992, p308), particularly in terms of their ability to communicate one's societal position, to others. The products of MVO tend to inhabit the shallows of our material worlds, as opposed to the very different mode of engagement occurring at the depths. In this way, it is clear that material possessions gain social meaning not only because they have instrumental use in sustaining and developing our daily lives but also because they function as symbols of identity, personality and self-expression (Dittmar & Pepper, 1994).

Down at the very depths of material experience, enduring associations between people and things are not wholly designable. After all, 'for personal reasons one can feel emotionally attached even to a turnip or a hubcap' (van Hinte, 1997, p234). This is because each user possesses a unique assemblage of memories and experiences, which render objects as vigorous symbols of the self, and carriers of great personal significance. Over 40-years earlier, Benedict in, *Patterns of Culture* (1955), asserted that '[n]o man ever looks at the world with pristine eyes. He sees it edited by a definite set of customs and institutions and ways of thinking (Benedict, 1955, p2).

Hadal or epipelagic – toward depth appropriate design

We can design for greater depths of emotional experience in several ways. We can specify materials that age gracefully, and that develop a quality and patina over time; functionality can also be approached in this way, whereby a product's performance and capability evolves and improves over time. We can design products that are easier to repair, upgrade and maintain. The challenge here is reframe the act of repair as a partisan act – a rich and integral aspect of the user experience. In the emotionally durable design

context, repair is forward-facing process of improvement, not one simply of reverting back to a former state. These are just a few emotionally durable design strategies, and while some of these come at an increased cost to manufacturers, they generate revenue downstream, through the introduction of service and upgrade.

It sounds peculiar to be proposing a commercial environment in which we encourage people to keep products for longer, and therefore sell less products! This, in many ways, runs contrary to the dominant model of capitalism; a fairly superficial idea, in which the more you sell equates to the level of success you have attained. However, we can look at this a different way. Take a pair of Puma sneakers, for example. One thing we know about these sneakers is that one-day, at some point in their life, they will wear out and the user (or, *consumer*, as economists like to call them) will need to replace them; that much, we know. However, what we don't know is which brand the user will choose? Will they replace them with a nice new pair from Puma, or will they be less loyal, and try a pair of Nikes this time? So often we hear opposition against longer-lasting products being based on such a story, where brand managers feel concerned that encouraging people to keep things for longer will affect the bottom-line. However there is a deep assumption lurking here, which is that repeat purchases will be with you, and that your customers are, indeed, brand loyal. I argue that by allowing customers to keep their products for longer, you nurture a deeper relationship with both the product and the brand, and in so doing, increase the likelihood of brand loyalty maturing. In this way, emotionally durable design can be seen as a commercially viable strategy for sustaining and growing market share, through building customer loyalty.

Until recently sustainable design methodologies have seldom engaged with the more fundamental questions such as the meaning and place of products in our lives, and the contribution of materials goods to what might be broadly termed, the human endeavour (Walker, 2006). Indeed, simply having more stuff stopped making people in Britain happier decades ago. The New Economics Foundation (NEF) argue for an economy of better, not more. One of things that last and can be repaired many times before being recycled, allowing us to share better the surplus of stuff we already have (NEF, 2012). We are currently experiencing a seismic shift in thinking, from the design and delivery of short-life products, to that of longer-lasting material experiences and services. It follows, then, that during product development, designers and manufacturers have a moral obligation to consider longevity and minimized lifecycle impacts (Van Nes & Cramer, 2005; Cooper, 2005). Consumers need to be aware of life spans and lifecycle impacts when buying products (Cooper & Christer, 2005).

Designing longer-lasting products without a clear understanding of the depth at which you are engaging users, is like packing a suitcase for a trip to an unknown destination, and not knowing what you will be doing when you get there. The picture is incomplete,

and forces gross generalisations to be made. As stated earlier, there are clear discrepancies between the products that matter, and the products we deploy as signifiers of identity and social position, for example. In conflating these two aspects of material experience, results risk distortion, and insight becomes misleading, and the impact of product life research is limited.

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Shared decision making: Empathic encounters between design and healthcare

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Abstract This paper explores the role of design in the context of shared decision making (SDM). Through a reflection of the terms 'human centred design' and 'patient centred care', the negotiation of human beings' roles and experiences in both disciplines is highlighted. As a tool for reflection, this paper discusses a pilot study in SDM for breast cancer patients. The research shows that the systemic complexity of healthcare is well aligned to design's contemporary positioning as a social, participatory endeavour linking people as design partners. The project suggests that the meeting of the two disciplines will profit the most if mutual learnings in methods, language and approaches are seen as part of the added project value and are given room in the design process. Design brief, process and team are three key matters which require alignment towards a more rounded understanding of patients as co-creating the meaning of a healthcare system. By evidence of this pilot study, we argue that design has the means to objectify healthcare obstacles and might thus add tangibility to critical debates on a systemic level.

Keywords Healthcare, Shared decision making, Co-design, Participatory innovation, People centred care

Introduction

Traditionally, collaborations between healthcare and design focused on artefacts, see for example Bruce Archer's standard design for hospital beds (Archer 1964; Lawrence 2002), the attempt to *design out* medical error (West et al 2013) and design interventions that focus on the delivery of healthcare in the realm of co-designing services (Carr et al 2009; Freire et al 2010; Sangiorgi 2011). The complexity of manifold standpoints and the effort of negotiating new, participatory roles in healthcare such as required by SDM is an aspect that has had a surprisingly little amount of coverage in design research literature (Bowen et al 2013; Donetto et al 2015) and is consequently the focus of this paper. SDM aims at integrating patient's own preferences into treatment pathways, as a consequence individual need and mainstream systems meet.

Current decision-making models

SDM argues that healthcare professionals as the only parties with access to evidence is no longer plausible – instead SDM presupposes more equality, respecting patients values and healthcare professional's recommendation (see Légaré et al, 2014:6). Multidisciplinary research shows that involving patients in shared decision making can improve health outcome, patient satisfaction, adherence to treatment, reduces patient complaints and improves patients' knowledge and empowerment (see Légaré et al 2014).¹ This latest Cochrane Review also points to the pitfalls of the 39 studies reviewed: data on evaluation is scarce, consequently little is still known which activities work best. In SDM, approaches are diverse with two main variances: they either focus on the

conversational situation between patient and clinician or offer an information system that can be used by patients themselves. Examples for the latter are option grids that guide patients through questions and lead to a profile with a suggested treatment option. Tools that focus stronger on the quality of the conversation between patient and clinician include Magic App (UK) (see Elwyn et al 2010) and cards and similar analogue decision aids developed by the Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research (US) (see Breslin et al 2008). From a designer's point of view, existing decision aids face difficulties on several levels: (1) Inclusivity, (2) a lack of a holistic integration of people's experiences and (3) their dependency on large-scale systemic dynamics. In terms of inclusivity, decision aids are typically heavily text based, as a digital source as well as on an analogue level. This strong reliance on reading abilities is critical given the diversity of people using healthcare systems. Secondly, it has been assumed that decision aids are best understood as helping the individual to find personally suited decisions. In fact existing aids target treatment options but individual experiences and socio-economic factors are hardly taken into consideration. It is known though that individual mobility or the level of family support, influences decision making. And third: Design and healthcare

1 Légaré's et al's claims on shared decision making with patients, needs to be treated with some caution in terms of the contexts in which this is appropriate. It is for example important to highlight instances where this is inappropriate such as in psychosis.

Design by People	Healthcare by People
Co-Creation Co-Design	SDM People Centred Care
Designer as Facilitator of Design Processes	Clinicians as Facilitator of Decision Processes

Design with People	Healthcare with Patients
User Centred Design	Patient Centred Care
Stakeholders become Active Partners	Knowledge Transfer via Health Literacy

Design for People	Healthcare for Patients
Designer Centred	Clinician Centred

Figure 1. Through the lens of for, with and by.

distinguish different levels of participation (see next section), but in order to enable a transformative quality of participation, systemic dynamics cannot be solved on a local level. Communication skills of clinicians, the knowledge about SDM or the timeframe allowed for decision making mark a few of these systemic parameters.

Co-design as a re-definition of roles

Jane Fulton Suri (2007) offered the terms designing for, with and by people pointing to different relationships with people in the design process. The approach designing *for* perceives people as experts and consults them during the design process. Designing *with* people means a greater involvement of people in the design process, with stakeholders becoming increasingly active partners. Designing *by* people points to a shift of roles and responsibilities with designers becoming facilitators of design processes and people getting the authorization for making their own design decisions (Fulton Suri 2007). This most radical move in design practice calling for sharing tools and design knowledge with non-designers has also been reflected widely by contemporary design research (Simonsen&Robertson 2013; Sanders&Stappers 2008, 2014). Sanders and Stappers argue that whereas the design process is linear in user-centred approaches, roles gets mixed up in co-design: ‘the person who will eventually be served through the design process is given the position of “expert of his/her experience” and plays a large role in knowledge development, idea generation and concept development’ (Sanders&Stappers, 2008:12).

The equivalent shift in thinking in healthcare

When looking at healthcare through the lens of for, with and by people (Figure 1), we can see parallels of a strikingly similar development. Healthcare moved from a modernist idea of welfare and good healthcare provision for everybody to an attempt of moving tools and evidence to the patient and the general public. In the logic of this terminology, healthcare for patients focuses on problem solving and on the delivery of

healthcare services being safe and effective; design projects in the area of patient safety and improving guidance systems in hospitals reflect this approach. Design is the supportive discipline in this respect, enabling goods, environments and services to be accessed by patients in the best possible way. Healthcare with patients can be linked to the idea of raising health literacy and transferring knowledge to the ‘empowered and expert patient’ (see Holmström&Röing 2010, Badcott 2005, Tyreman 2005, Civan and Pratt 2007 for a discussion on the limitations and advances of ‘The Expert Patient’).² Healthcare by patients would mark the most advanced development centering on the idea of shared decision making and patient democracy. While this participatory model is taken from design, parallel approaches in healthcare can be found in sources provided by the UK’s Centre for Patient Leadership, the New Economics Foundation, NESTA, the King’s Fund or the UK Design Council ‘Double Diamond’ Discover-Define-Develop-Deliver model for healthcare demonstration projects. The Centre for Patient Leadership for example offers individual patients as well as organisations, workshops with mentoring and coaching support, and focus on self-leadership, relationship building and dialogue, and developing influencing and advocacy skills, to enhance patient

2 In the history of healthcare the development of the terms ‘person-centred’ and ‘client-centred’ also relate to the work of the psychologist Dr. Carl Rogers (1902 – 1987). Initially developed as a form of psychotherapy, its principles of empathy and congruence were transferred to other areas such as patient care. The expert patient movement is one example for this development in its search for what constitutes a patient’s expertise or to what extent a weaker notion of authority would support a more egalitarian system. The limitations and advances of a non-judgmental and empathic relationship in healthcare correlate with SDM.

engagement.³ The skills sharing approach can be compared to passing on tools in co-creation or co-design processes.

SDM through the lens of participatory innovation

The focus of healthcare and design shows that both disciplines share a similar development from doctor and designer centred to a people centred approach, from closed specialist processes to open ones. However, cross-disciplinary collaboration bears both real-world and conceptual questions. Participatory design/innovation offers a framework that considers the diversity of language, conversation styles and methods as windows of opportunities and is thus discussed as a potential lens for approaching collaborations between design and clinical healthcare.

'Boundary' difficulties, opportunities and empathic encounters

Studies in design and innovation management reflect on various challenges met by corporations and non-profit organizations trying to implement more open and participatory approaches to innovation. Carlile (2002) argued that conflict arises at knowledge boundaries, meaning that knowledge is highly localized and embedded, causing conflict when working across functions. Stacey and Griffin (2005) see organizations in a steady interplay between inclusion and exclusion of different stakeholders with different identities and beliefs. In line with this discourse in organizational management, Sproedt and Larsen claim that "(...) the innovation process emerges not as a result of one singular idea or intention, but in the meeting of differences" (Sproedt&Larsen, 2012:1004). Fonseca (2002) explains in this context that innovation is an ongoing process of understanding and misunderstanding project partners. The emergence of conflict is thereby perceived as opportunity, spotlighting constraints and 'conversations in the shadow' (see Larsen&Bogers 2014) as a productive source of novelty and innovation, rather than as failed approaches of co-operations. 'In the local, emerging interaction people negotiate meaning of knowledge and make sense of novelty' (Sproedt&Larsen, 2012:1005). Via the pilot study covered in this paper we reflect on some of the themes discussed in participatory innovation and do so by observations on a collaboration between a Danish hospital group and the design development department 'Social Inclusion'⁴ of the first author's design institution.

Table 1. Methods.

Project Phase	Methods	Time Frame
Collect	Project-Setup, Participant Observation, Patient Interviews, Desktop Research	2,5 Months
Comprehend	Analysis, Visualizing Data, Personas	1 Month
Conceptualize	Co-Creation Workshop, Prototyping	1 Month
Create	Communication Design, Testing	0,5 Month

Insights into how design and healthcare could collaborate in the best possible way are searched for along these research questions: What are the challenges and opportunities at the boundaries between different disciplines learning to work together (here design and clinical healthcare)? What role does participatory design play in the shift of power from top-down healthcare systems to one more democratically involving those individuals affected by decisions made? How could design support SDM in integrating patients' (often) emotional experiences into treatment pathways?

Method

This paper is based on a pilot study in SDM in breast cancer. The methods and process outline base on the human centred '5C MODEL' (Fries&Gelting 2014). The phases 'Collect' and 'Comprehend' follow the contemporary understanding of a human-centered design process including an observational phase to meet stakeholders in the context of the specific project (see also Blomberg et al 1993; Blomberg&Burrell 2009). 'Conceptualize' and 'Create' point to ideation and innovation phase (the fifth C 'Collaborate' forms a connecting theme). (Table 1)

The design work has been carried out by the design development team, while the first author of this paper had an observer role. The design team observed 36 patient-doctor consultations at the hospital. Participant observation was followed by 15 semi-structured interviews focusing on treatment plans, information and options. The design team's desktop research focused on brochures and information material that patients usually receive from the hospital. (Table 2)

The limitations of this pilot study have to be acknowledged fully on several levels: due to the hospital's clinical pathways only eight patients of the observed 36 formed part of the target patient group (newly diagnosed breast cancer patients offered post-operative prophylactic chemotherapy and/or anti-hormone therapy to help prevent disease relapse). A questionnaire was sent out to involved physicians, nurses and the design team by the design researcher after the end of the five-month project, informing them that responses will be anonymized and used to gather project learnings for shaping potential future

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- Doughty, one of the founders of The Centre for Patient Leadership says: "It's about building effective relationships, being able to communicate and having the ability to dialogue ... and talking together about problems that you share. We are about giving patients the confidence and the skills to engage with other professionals in which the patient themselves perceive themselves as being equal." (The Guardian, accessed 20 March 2016).
 - The design development departments at Design School Kolding focus on three labs, the Lab for Social Inclusion focuses on prevention and welfare technology (see <https://www.designskolenkolding.dk/en/lab-social-inklusion>).

collaborations. The questionnaire used open format questions to give the respondents the opportunity to express their opinions in an unrestricted mode, including open-ended questions seeking suggestions for improvements in future projects.

While all three designers responded, only one clinician gave formal feedback. Patient satisfaction has not been evaluated because the tool has not been implemented yet.

The paper aims for analytical generalization by reflecting on notes and experiences in search for patterns of interaction between the collaborative partners. The following sections describe the design process in chronological order as observed by the authors of this paper; they therefore represent subjective viewpoints.

A tool for shared decision making in breast cancer

Healthcare demographics in Denmark

The collaborative hospital partner is a cancer and university centre in Denmark planning to gain expertise and knowledge on SDM and to establish a knowledge centre within the hospital group. In the past few years, hospitals in Danish healthcare have seen increasing centralization and specialization (Olejaz et al 2012). 'In this attempt to optimize and standardize treatment and care in large specialized hospital units, the individual patients' needs and preferences may be lost' (Dahl Steffensen, 2015:3). A baseline study commissioned by the hospital underlines that cancer patients want to participate in decisions about their treatment. According to the survey every fifth lacked the opportunity to participate and healthcare professionals pointed to the absence of tools to perform SDM during their consultations (Olsen et al, 2013 a and b). In respect to cancer patients who generally receive potent and potentially hazardous treatments involving various healthcare settings and several healthcare professionals '(...) this makes it essential to discuss with the individual patient potential harms and benefits of different treatment options, including the option not to treat' (Dahl Steffensen, 2015:3).

Table 2. Stakeholder Chart.

Stakeholders	Number and further Specification
Patients	36 (with 8 from main target group)
Clinicians	10 (5 oncologists, 5 nurses)
Designers	3 (with specialization in communication, service and product design)
Design Researcher	1 (specialized in welfare design)
Steering Group	7 (Head of Innovation, Research Management, Healthcare Researchers, Clinicians, Director of Centre of Shared Decision Making)
Administrative Worker	1 (admin background)

The design process: From kick-off to final presentation

Project pre-phase

An initial planning group suggested working on a tool for guiding patients' decisions on whether to participate in a clinical trial or to receive standard treatment. Administration changed this initial focus to the current task, described below. Additionally to a change of project focus, the collaboration started before the knowledge center for SDM was established and obtained knowledge.

Project kick-off

The design brief for the first collaboration in the field of SDM between hospital and design school focused on the development of a decision tool for use at the Department of Oncology in their work with newly diagnosed breast cancer patients. The project's time frame was five months. In the kick-off meeting, project leaders from Design Development Department and the hospital, the innovation manager and clinicians were present. The meeting centred on framing the working process based on the briefing received from the hospital. The project leader from the design school focused on the process such as access to patients and clinicians as a basis for a user-centered design process. The director of the SDM knowledge center emphasized her wish for a tool implementable in clinical pathways: 'I don't want this tool to sit on the shelf. I want it to be used in the clinic.' There has been no discussion at this point about sufficient time to meet this goal and no issues around the content of the design brief were raised. The design project leader has developed a design process description based on the meeting.

Month 2 Skype interview with one of the designers

The status quo of the project was discussed in a talk between the first author of this paper and one of the designers. From the designers' point of view the project steps and responsibilities seemed straight forward as planned in the design brief. Nevertheless uncertainty arose when concrete appointments were to be made for interviews with stakeholders, more precisely with cancer patients. The designer reflected on these challenges with the planned interviews:

Nobody was in charge of telling the patients.
(Designer#1)

While contacts to clinicians had been established at the first meeting and beyond, the contact to patients was out of reach for the design team, they relied on the hospital to organize them. In the same talk, the designer reflected on first findings and design opportunities, thus at this point of the project the design team had participated in 15 patient consultations.

They [the patients] want the doctors to decide. (...) Nobody says no to treatment. There is too much information, so what is missing is a tool to remember information. (Designer#1)

Based on these observations, the mismatch of design

Figure 2. Ideation of three dimensional 'changeable roadmap'.

brief and field observations became obvious for the design team. These consultations aimed at post-operative prophylactic therapies given to lower the risk of the cancer coming back. These therapies preventing a cancer relapse offered only two options – treat or not treat. Following the logic of SDM and the design brief, 'treat' or 'not treat' would have been the two options for the decision tool. One of the main design opportunities was though located as a tool capable of documenting the information given at the consultation.

Month 3 Presentation of three concepts

The focus of this meeting was the presentation of the design process thus far and a discussion on how and with which concept to proceed. This time, participants also included the steering group. Via an analysis of designer's observations, twelve themes ranging from 'horror stories', 'information' or 'letter from the hospital', 'a lot of words', 'preparation', 'common agenda', 'which info when' were clustered. During the presentation the design team supported the themes with quotes from their interviewees. In order to make the types of patients more tangible, the design team worked with three personas: 'Vera, 61, positive', 'Mette, 44, confused' and 'Henriette, 36, critical' were chosen as representatives for typical patients and their experiences, emotions and socio-economic background, their trust in the clinician, how they react to the consultation and if they brought relatives with them to the meeting or not. The method of personas, that considers social-economic aspects of the design target group (a common but also criticized tool in design practice, see Tonkinwise 2011), was recognized by the clinicians as a precise rendering of their patient group. Finally the design team presented the spaces of opportunity organized around the three concepts: preparation tool, common agenda and remembering tool. The debate among meeting participants was on whether to focus on a qualification tool ('preparation') or a remembering tool. One idea vividly discussed amongst the meeting members focused on a 'changeable roadmap' (Figure 2), a tool that could start from an empty road at the beginning of the consultation and be filled up with treatments and

Figure 3. Generating ideas at the workshop.

procedures as agreed upon between clinician and patient. The clinicians as well as other meeting members added ideas to this concept.

The design team tested the idea of the 'changeable roadmap' with three-dimensional bricks but regarded a game-like tool as inappropriate for the subject of cancer in an adult patient group.

Month 4 Co-creation workshop

The workshop took place at the hospital and brought together patients and relatives, three doctors and three nurses; it was chaired by the design team and supported by design students that helped facilitating and visualizing the process and group work (Figure 3).

After presenting the schedule, the designers shared their process and findings with the workshop team (in a similar way as the presentation at the steering group meeting), afterwards mixed teams and discussed questions such as: 'How do you define shared decision making?' and 'Please give an everyday example of SDM.' As the next task team members were asked to individually note down their thoughts on the three basic design concepts so far, a preparation tool, common agenda and remembering tool. After a presentation in symposium, every member could choose a favourite concept to proceed with for an individual idea brainstorm focusing on wishes and ideas for the specific concept. All ideas were clustered and structured into one big poster. The team members were asked to vote again for one of the generated ideas; the 'winner' was discussed in more depth, focusing on form and content of a potential solution. Finally one design student each drew and visualized their team's solution showing how the idea could work step by step. A presentation and discussion followed. Group One developed the idea of a 'Patient Bag' that provides the road map for the patient journey ahead. Group Two proposed an app that visualized the treatment pathway and Group Three presented symbolic representation of the therapies divided in three categories. What united all three approaches was the support for cancer patients with information that might eliminate some of the emotional concerns, questions and uncertainties.

Figure 4. The introduction sheet.

Figure 5. Conversational sheet 2_oncologist's page.

Figure 6. Conversational sheet 2_nurse's page.

Month 5 Final presentation

Based on the analysis of fieldwork and co-creation workshop the team decided to prototype a tool that shall unite a preparation, qualification, conversation and checking tool in one. To be used during the physician consultations this first proposal consists of an A4 introduction and two A3 conversation sheets. Before the consultation, the patient receives the introduction sheet which provides a visual overview of the elements of the consultation (Figure 4) along with the notice letter. These five main areas cover health status (1), further treatment (2), medical examination (3), good advice (4) and start of treatment (5). During the consultation, clinicians and patient cover the five consultation elements using the two conversation sheets (Figure 5 and 6). Doctors, nurses and patients shall fill out the sheets together and thereby actively share information. The final proposal is also a means for communicating and informing family and kin in a brief way – a decisive aspect in a socially challenging life phase. The final proposal is also a means for communicating and informing family and kin in a brief way – a decisive aspect in a socially challenging life phase.

Analysis

The data that has been acquired rests on knowledge from the design process, observations by the design researcher following the process, as well as the analysis of the questionnaire sent out to designers and clinicians after the project. The limitations of this pilot study have been discussed in the method's section, the following analysis should therefore be viewed as learnings for a second study following this one. The three main areas of interest for emerging design opportunities are explored in the following:

The design brief and its relation to the outcome

When analysing the project and looking at the brief, it becomes evident that it frames the task very precisely but that there is a mismatch between brief and actual clinical encounter, they did not harmonize. The questionnaire quotes from both clinicians and designers support these observations:

(...) the aim of this project was changed centrally from the administration (...) the decision making situation was changed to a situation where the patient do not have a real choice between several options – it was instead a treat or not to treat decision. (Clinician)

The goal of the project did not fit into the real world, meaning that shared decision takes place in another part of the patients journey. (Designer#2)

The fact that a design brief does not represent the most demanding problem is a well-known aspect in many design projects. User centred design thus bases its concepts on fieldwork, which this project also did. This approach indicates that design briefs frame the desired direction of the outcome but they do not prescribe the medium or form because this can only be decided in the course of the project. The more precise picture the design team gains, the clearer the problem becomes, and the more clearly a possible solution can be described. Design research discusses this as the 'co-evolution' of problem and solution (see Rittel&Webber 1973 for an early discussion of 'wicked problems' and Buchanan 1992 and Coyne 2005 for more recent ones). A crucial finding is that the tool targets primarily the recall of medical information rather than the decision making process. The medical decision has to be taken earlier in the patient

journey. The current first proposal is an objectification of the patient journey in this given health care system. An enhanced permeability from bottom-up (instead of a top-down understanding of health care systems) is thus eligible. Small-scale observations as made in this pilot study, might point to vital systemic obstacles (e.g. the time allowed for decision making). Participatory design loose strength, if broader systemic topics are not questioned more widely.

The design process

Designers all pointed to the tight time frame that did not foresee enough resources for testing; the clinician also recognized a lack of touchpoints but did not link it with a problem in the set timeframe but rather the team set-up. This lack of time is also reflected on at several points in the questionnaires:

I am a little worried about the next phase, no time or considerations have been made about the implementation process. (...) Next time there should be a strategy for execution of the designed product.

Producing prototypes is the best tool for understanding the end product. These processes take time, and we needed more time to test. (Designer#2)

After the stakeholder workshop which took place after the Concept Presentation, no further meeting was scheduled and no time was reserved for an implementation phase with testing and iterative design adaptations. The meeting structure between project steering group and design team took place in the following way (Figure 7):

Figure 7. The meeting structure.

By evidence of this pilot study, future collaborations' time frame should be more realistic. The 5C Model used by the design team lacks an implementation and evaluation phase. As part of a more robust study design for the following project, this model shall thus be complemented by participatory process models (Simonsen and Hertzum 2012) more effective in health care settings.

The team and missing resources

The analysis of the process points to further human resources' positions that would have been beneficial. For sustainable future projects, more resources should be ensured for integrating learnings from existing international projects as well as supporting evaluation, implementation and dissemination with a research perspective. This research resource would better frame the concept of SDM and equip the design team with an advanced knowledge base. Although there was a third party administrative worker

assigned, this project showed that it needs a clinical insider to coordinate stakeholders and, more importantly, to communicate the project vision internally and externally.

When asking for missing competencies in the project set-up in the questionnaire, the clinician puts it forward in the following way:

Implementation team and team for sustaining the project (...). Ideas for future perspectives – what are the next steps? How to measure and evaluate whether the product has made a difference to the patients and to the clinicians. (Clinician)

A health researcher providing a system for evaluation and measurement should be included in future projects to ensure an active learning culture alongside the design researcher.

Everybody in the design team mentioned the emotional weight of being confronted with cancer patients' individual cases. Providing the opportunity for mediation sessions seems an evident necessity to allow for reflection and supervision of designers working with cancer patients.

Discussion

What can this pilot study demonstrate for collaborative encounters between design and SDM in healthcare on a wider scale? A collaborative project set-up can be viewed as a tool for knowledge transfer and this is inherently ridden with constraints, including the messiness of multiple viewpoints. Experience-based design in SDM should therefore acknowledge disagreement and conflict as productive part of a new 'anthropology of services' (see Blomberg and Darrah 2015). While SDM can be an object of design, it likewise requires the acknowledgement of design's boundaries. With SDM's nature of requiring enactment by all stakeholders, it expands the character of a finite service or product. This asks for an open-ended live lab and partial results rather than finished objects. In this respect a clear focus on implementation as an iterative process is essential and shall be ensured by robust study designs.

The greatest social gains lie in an ongoing exploration of the concept of shared decision making together with stakeholders. Mattelmäki et al (2011) argue for the significance of 'incompleteness of field study outcomes as it invites sense-making through (...) empathic understanding and engagement'. In a similar sense collaborative design is 'a process of exploring what it is that will create value for specific people' (Mattelmäki et al, 2011:79). New design briefs should include a collective exploration of the questions: What is the meaning of SDM in the local context? Healthcare research has the means to frame this definition and understanding; communication design can convert this into a strong identity supporting a collective ownership through a joint stakeholder narrative and experience. By evidence of this pilot study we regard this strategy as essential, thus local healthcare systems and people within the institutions determine if concept are used and implemented sustainably.

The most essential discussion and learning in this pilot study regards the interplay of local and large-scale dynamics in SDM. The project objectified one specific aspect of the current patient pathway and made it tangible through a first design proposal: Although the design brief asked for a decision tool, fieldwork showed that the medical decision is taken at another point on the clinical pathway. This fact raises questions such as: Is the time and support appropriate that is currently allowed for patients to make far fledged decisions? Are healthcare systems balancing the quest for mainstream pathways well with the individuality and experiences of its patients? What this pilot study shows is that the obstacles and misunderstandings of the two disciplines working together gave a clearer picture of large-scale systemic problems rather than only those on a local level. Patient activation, communication skills of clinicians, the level of knowledge about SDM in the wider public, mainstream healthcare pathways – they all challenge the application of SDM. Consequently, findings point to a need for tools that allow for systemic modification and change in healthcare. The difficulties related to this pilot study are thus symptoms, in need for careful examination towards a more experience driven practice. Future study designs need to be aware of notions of co-realization and discourses of infrastructuring in participatory design (see Star & Ruhleder 1996; Hartswood et al 2008, Karasti 2014).

Conclusion

Shared decision making is redefining a historically learned role-setting in hospitals. These shifts in status and power between clinicians and patients request a fundamental change in our understanding of healthcare in general. It calls for a swing of mind-sets in healthcare – ideally performed by all stakeholders connected to it. Participatory, empathic design acknowledges misunderstanding and conflict as the basis for novelty and advancement. However the power of participatory concepts such as SDM will be measured by its strength to impact healthcare systems' set structures more fundamentally from bottom-up, based on people's actual experiences.

This paper discussed the development of human centred design as a potential lens for looking at patient centred care. In design, *users* turned into *people* and *citizens*, based on a more holistic idea of working with people as co-creators of services and products. If healthcare aspires to implement shared decision making as a future standard, a shift in terminology towards *people* centred care would follow consequently. We call for further cross-disciplinary research into the practical, conceptual and political implications of the role of the patient in SDM. What methods support the involvement of emotional experiences in SDM is suggested as a potential area for future research in Design&Emotion. Critical evaluation of the collaboration between design and healthcare should consequently focus on the swing and constitution of power relations as esteemed in SDM.

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Design for human flourishing in architecture: Programmatic writing as a way to design socio-cultural affordances

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Abstract In architectural design for human flourishing (DfHF), compatibility between the environment and the user is crucial. A supportive relationship between the two is characterized by the environment's action possibilities and the user's perception thereof in terms of complementarity with the users' psychological needs and personal goals.

This paper highlights a design method called "programmatic writing", that was developed in a student design project. Programmatic writing connects target groups' needs and an enriched program within an architectural design, by applying techniques as narratives and scenario writing. This is a first crucial step in an architectural DfHF-process.

In this paper, first, a short theoretical background of DfHF and the set-up of the design project are sketched. Next, the development of the design method is discussed through an analysis of the design process in the exercise. Hereby, we aim to contribute to the development of an architectural DfHF-process.

Keywords *Architecture, Design for human flourishing, Design exercise, Programmatic writing, Affordances*

Introduction

Human flourishing is a topic in design research that is starting to receive attention today (e.g. Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013), but in the field of architecture, it remains rather underexposed (e.g. Delle Fave et al, 2011; Stevens et al, 2014, 2016a). As a design approach, design for human flourishing (DfHF) consequently could benefit from a theoretical basis that can be used to develop practical tools for architects to guide them to adopt this approach. In that respect, this paper discusses the development of the design method of "programmatic writing", with the purpose of introducing it as a possible method to be applied in an architectural DfHF-process.

A trajectory to design for human flourishing: designing spatial flourishing affordances

Recently, we have proposed a theoretical trajectory to design architecture for human flourishing, see Figure 1 (Stevens et al, 2016a). It takes an affordance-approach and is based on a re-interpretation of the Vitruvian architectural quality criterion of *Venustas*, that comprises the poetic, experiential properties of architecture, to anchor it in architectural theory. For the development of the theoretical trajectory, affordance theories -starting from the basic work of Gibson (1979), over Warren (1984), Norman (2002), Chemero (2003, 2009) and Rietveld and Kiverstein (2014)- are researched by the first author (a designer) from a humane angle, in order to capture what benefits an environmental affordance provides to its users, more particularly in terms of compliance with

users' needs. We noticed that over time, the affordance evolved from only responding to basic, instinctive and physical needs, towards including more cultural and psychological user characteristics. Our study on affordance theories concluded with introducing 'spatial flourishing affordances', a new, complete humane outlook on affordances. Spatial flourishing affordances can be defined as an environmental affordance that invites, incites and enthuses the user to undertake activities that the environment enables, in order to fulfil their psychological needs and personal goals. In that way, a person can be set on its way to flourishing (Stevens et al, 2016a). The trajectory is comprised of three main components that need to be treated by architects in a specific order. As Figure 1 demonstrates, first, the architect must invest in his 'target group', and collect psychological information regarding their needs, goals and daily goings. Next, these data need to be processed into an elaborate programming phase in which activities need to be designed, complying with the expectations, and psychological and socio-cultural needs and wants of the target group. Finally, the program needs to be translated into a material design, via architectural elements.

In DfHF, the responsibility of architects lies in creating architectural conditions under which a specific target group can flourish; in designing spaces that psychologically support, invite, enthuse and enable users to undertake meaningful actions, and thereby empower themselves and gain a positive effect

Figure 1. A theoretical trajectory to DfHF in architecture: designing spatial flourishing affordances.

on their flourishing. Note that this trajectory is not yet a design methodology. It provides architects with a general frame of reference to give direction to their architectural process, and assists them in practicing a new, more humane way of architectural thinking. This paper however is a first step in concretizing the trajectory. Through designerly and empirically exploring this proposed trajectory, we aim to distil useful and more concrete applicable information for architects, and formulate how they can work with the components in practice.

In the next chapters, we will describe the student design project “Layer Cake”, in which we aimed to create flourishing architecture for elderly persons by empathically designing social environments as seen *through their eyes*. We will analyse the design process with the use of Figure 1, the theoretical trajectory for human flourishing. Concretely, we will zoom in on the design of the ‘socio-cultural affordances’ that are created via the first two trajectory-components, that is, ‘target group’ and ‘program’ (visualized in the highlighted left part of Figure 1). Next, we discuss the development of the design method of programmatic writing that evolved from unravelling the design steps that students took in working with ‘target group’ and ‘program’. To conclude, we propose programmatic writing as a design method that architects can apply in order to create socio-cultural affordances and by that, take concrete measures to DfHF.

Design studio project “Layer Cake”

Layer Cake was a two-week fulltime master class in architectural DfHF, organized in February 2014. The task was to design social programs for a high-rise residential building for people over 60 years, comprised of 40 residential floors (containing private apartments, service flats or even care rooms) interlarded with 10 ‘public floors’ with a variety in social programs, see Figure 2. The ten public floor designs formed the design exercise, and needed to (1) assist residents in flourishing, (2) address the entire group of residents, differing in physical and other age-related characteristics, and (3) root the building socially in the neighbouring urban fabric. The design

brief had an overarching humane character; neither further programmatic demands nor spatial end terms were formulated. The exercise focused on the experiential character of spaces. Ten design groups were each comprised of four master students in interior architecture, and each group was attributed one public floor of the high-rise living tower to configure into a ‘social layer’ meeting the humane design brief.

Designing socio-cultural affordances, tested in Layer Cake

In the exercise Layer Cake, students were obliged to spend the first design week entirely on their ‘social concept’, by which we mean they had to select a basic social function for their floor, developing it further into a number of meaningful activities and experiences that fit the needs of the target group. Communication of these intangible design results was also an important factor. Altogether, the designing of these so-called ‘socio-cultural affordances’ formed the centre of gravity of the exercise. Only in the second week we asked students to make an actual spatial translation, by 3D modelling, and thereby transforming the program into an architectural 3D design. In this paper, we will only discuss the first design week, namely designing the ‘social concept’, in which the design method of programmatic writing was developed. In terms of the trajectory, this implies working with the design components ‘target group’ and ‘program’, as visualized in the highlighted left part of Figure 1.

Below, we will explain the development of the design method programmatic writing, by unravelling the students’ design process per component of the trajectory. More in detail, per component we first present short theoretical insights that were valuable and applicable to incorporate in the design process. Secondly, we present how these insights were inserted in the set-up of the design exercise. Thirdly, we discuss in what way the students received and handled these insights in the actual design process.

The ten design projects in Layer Cake:

1. Jong geleerd oud gedaan
2. Ex Libris
3. Marktforum
4. Grootmoeders keuken
5. Sport-o-rama
6. Tussen de soep en de patatten
7. Spotted
8. Herinnering als vorm van ontplooiing
9. Theater in het park
10. Een (her)beleving

Figure 2. Layer Cake: a photo of the scale model, a sketch of the tower and a list of the ten designed projects that came out of the exercise.

Component one Target group: defining target group specifics

Theory

To empathically connect with their target group, architects need specific experiential information: daily goings, hopes and fears, aspirations, etcetera. Architects have at least two options in gathering this kind of psychological information: collect data themselves, or consult academic sociological data regarding the target group.

In the first option of gathering information themselves, many methods come to mind. Architects that design small projects for a single client, for instance living spaces, are familiar with asking clients for their daily routines, or they build on their own intuition or predicate upon personal 'living' experiences to empathize with clients. This is what Juhani Pallasmaa refers to when stating: *"The only proper way to deal with the everyday practice of architecture is that the architect becomes the client him- or herself"* (Havik & Tielens, 2013, p. 41). However, when the 'client' is not a single family requesting a design for a house, but a varied audience in a (semi-) public building such as residential care, architects needs to tap into other approaches, since empathizing with a more abstract and undefined client does not come natural. Additionally, architects in formation are barely confronted with psychological and social sciences (e.g. Oppliger, 2015), which impedes the interpretation of socio-cultural knowledge and its inclusion in a spatial design process.

With Layer Cake, we attempted to overcome this burden for architects, by applying techniques from narrative theory and thereby integrating the user into the design process, not as a co-designer but as a sort of narrator. Parnell (2003) already argued that listening to clients and communicating with people from day one in the design process, can help architecture students to see their perspective on design and value them within the design, and Till (2005) recognizes the power of simple, ordinary conversations in search for new methods of communication with clients in design. Gerards and De Bleeckere (2014) have already successfully brought these insights into a design exercise with architecture

students, and developed narrative thinking as an anchor throughout the design process and a help to connect designers and users. In this respect, narratives show potential to get to know future users and make an empathic connection. We believe narratives contribute to profiling and personifying unknown clients, which in DfHF can help architects to make more empathized design decisions. DfHF is designing meaningful activities that are in accordance with the users' psychological needs and personal goals; personal narratives linked to the users as such, can be viewed as a valuable tool to set designers on a path to designerly thinking in terms of activities and usage patterns, rooted in the living environment of the user. This could lead to more daring and creative design solutions. We thereby felt that narratives are a suitable method to be included in the design process of component one, 'target group', in the exercise.

In the second option, namely that architects would apply data from scientific research, they often struggle with the format under which data are presented; these are often written in a language that architects are not acquainted with and this kind of knowledge is not directly applicable in design processes. However, implementing research data can assist designers in fulfilling their humane task, but only when the research is directed at and serving to the architect's work. As researchers in human flourishing, earlier the authors have developed a framework containing psychological information important for flourishing of the target group of elderly persons.

Layer Cake – set up

Before the start of the exercise, we asked the four students in each design group to gather narratives from the target group, that is, personal stories containing psychological and experiential information from respectively four elderly persons. Since we aimed for coverage of the varied, heterogeneous group of elderly people, the four students were asked to each cover a resident residing in one of the following four types of elderly housing: (1) living independently at home, (2) residing with family members or living at home and receiving help, (3) residing in an assisted living initiative and (4) living in a residential care centre (RCC). The purpose was for the students to get a grip on the daily activities, life aspirations, hopes, and

fears of elderly people regarding their present and future.

In addition to the collected narratives, the authors provided the students with a framework called ‘the building blocks of elderly flourishing’ that was composed after a review of gerontology literature in four key journals in the field of aging research: Journal of Aging Studies, Aging International, Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics and the International Journal of Gerontology. This literature review was conducted to upload each of the five items of the acronym and well-being-model P.E.R.M.A. (Seligman, 2011) with specifications regarding the target group of elderly persons (Stevens et al, 2016b). The building blocks of elderly flourishing contain specific psychological information, and explicate 17 important psychological needs of this target group that are important for their flourishing, see Table 1. We purposefully described the psychological information under the format of ‘strategies’ or generalist actions which elderly persons can undertake, in a way that it is understandable for architects and can be applied together with narratives in a design process focusing on designing meaningful activities.

Layer Cake – student’s design process

Students collected narratives from their target group via in-depth interviews. In addition, some gave the elderly person a diary to fill in, accompanied the interviewee on daily activities, etcetera. Coming to the design workshop with their collected narratives, we asked each design group to set up a think process in which they had to distil a main ‘generic’ social topic for their spatial layer in Layer Cake out of the narratives. Students first came up with for instance a library, a museum or a garden. The proposed functions are all closely linked to the traditional living habits of educating, entertaining, relaxing, etcetera. By using the real-life narrative information from the elderly population as the base to select a social topic, Layer Cake’s design and its affordances are a direct response

to actual concerns, hopes and wishes from this target group.

In the analysis of the gathered narratives, it became clear that respondents gave information in six categories: ‘ambitions for the future’, ‘activities that had to be given up’, ‘current hobbies’, ‘something that gives meaning’, ‘important objects’ and ‘favourite location’. The first four categories contain intangible, experiential information, the latter two contain tangible information with a spatial undertone. In the students’ processing of the data with the purpose of defining a generic social topic to design their social layer around, we noticed that they did not automatically search for the most frequently occurring activities, but often empathically chose for one interesting quote or a remarkable social activity an interviewee tried to maintain. For instance, in the project “Ex Libris” one interviewee living in a service flat mentioned she visits the adjoining RCC once a month to volunteer with a small book cart from the local library to accommodate RCC residents with books. She is also still active as a lector in her parish. Empathically, students were drawn to this anecdotal fact, and then searched their data for aspects that could be linked to the topic of reading. Eventually, they decided to further develop ‘library’ as their social topic. Another approach other students took was seeking for a ‘general truth’ in the data, a main topic that was present throughout all personal details and anecdotes. The ‘general truth’ behind the topic was distilled by students out of the different ways the interviewees handled or executed it. For instance in the project “Sport-o-rama”, students found that sports was a recurring topic, and their interviewees had different relations to a sport experience: ranging from watching sports on television, simulating sports on the x-box, actively practising sports, etcetera. Other student groups tried to distil experiences that provided meaning out of their data, for instance the design group of project “Jong geleerd oud gedaan”, noticed that their interviewees all valued getting together with family or friends, preferably in the cosiness of their own living room. Bringing the two together, led to their topic of a large public ‘living room’ equipped with homemade or second-life furniture.

Table 1. The 17 building blocks of elderly flourishing, in five overarching themes.

Overarching theme	Building blocks
BEING ACTIVE – CHALLENGE YOURSELF	Train & master existing skills
	Execute hobbies
	Engage in meaningful activities Develop new skills -> challenge!
SOCIALLY ACTIVE IN A NETWORK	Solidarity & empathy
	Productive role in society
	Built & invest in social network
IDENTITY ENFORCING	Reminiscence
	Narratives
	Mindfulness & spirituality
BEING VISIBLE TO THE WORLD - COUNTING IN	Sharing knowledge, items, hobbies
	Volunteering & charity
	Organizational involvement: having a role in community
STAYING ENGAGED WITH LIFE – SELF-MAINTAINING	Resourcefulness – adaptation
	Exercise control
	Goals & individual choices
	Engagement with life

After the processing of the narratives, we asked students to build further on their generic social topic, and include and interpret the *building blocks of elderly flourishing* we had given them. This moment formed the transition between component one ‘target group’ and component two ‘program’. In the next part, we will discuss in detail how students in cooperation with the first author developed methods to transform the generic social topic into a social concept and an enriched program to assist the target group in flourishing, with the use of the building blocks framework.

Component two Program: Designing an enriched program

Theory

In DfHF the designed activities must provide meaning for the target group; even the most banal activities can become meaningful if they are connected to and fulfil certain psychological needs of users (Desmet & Hassenzahl, 2012; Hassenzahl et al, 2013).

In transforming a generic social topic into a set of qualitative activities, in the viewpoint of the authors, the theory of narratives can be applied yet again, however in a different manner. Instead of the target group recalling life events and sharing life experiences, architects now have to create experiences and new 'memories', for instance via storytelling. Consequently, in architecture, inventing and writing out new narratives in the form of daily schedules, storyboards or usage patterns helps to enrich activities experientially. Since DfHF is based on fulfilling psychological needs, it is essential to find activities that can fulfil these needs. In other words, activities should incite specific behaviours in people. We believe that when designerly handling this, interesting links can be found with the theory on design for behaviour change (e.g. Fogg, 2009). We do not directly aim for behaviour change in DfHF, but the two have in common that they both aim to encourage people to undertake certain pre-designed activities, that incite an internal process; whether that process is behaviour change or flourishing. Fogg's model for design for behaviour change (2009) can be useful to include in designing activity patterns for flourishing; it demonstrates that intensity, frequency and duration are important aspects that activities need to be measured up to if the purpose is inducing positive internal change. These factors can assist designers in deepening the experience within their activities. In DfHF, we feel that all three factors are inherently linked to the natural differentiation within heterogeneous target groups such as 'elderly persons', differing in mental, physical and many other characteristics. Consequently, these users are in need of variations in intensity, frequency and duration within an activity to keep it interesting and successful to all.

Layer Cake – set up

Next to the insights borrowed from design for behaviour change and narrative theory, the framework of *building blocks of elderly flourishing* was used as input in Layer Cake's set up. The framework was inserted in the design process as a base to anticipate on specific behaviours and to start designing activity patterns. Concretely, it presented students the psychological needs and desired behaviours they had to fulfil. Narrative theory provided students with a method that stimulated thinking in terms of scenarios and activity patterns that provide users with a variety of 'chances' (activities) to fulfil their needs. The insights from design for behaviour change had the purpose of designing activities that speak to the entire target group, and respond to differentiation (e.g. physical and mental characteristics, age).

In that matter, the set up should stimulate students to enrich and add extra layers to the generic social topic they pinpointed in step one of the design exercise, in a way that it supports the target group in flourishing. Notwithstanding theoretical insights from other design branches are useful in architecture, we needed to search for a systematic way to combine knowledge and design so-called meaningful activities in architecture. Since this approach requests a new design attitude, the authors opted to co-work with students in finding ways to design these meaningful activities and desired behaviours. We gave students the remaining four days of design week 1 to transfer their social topic into an enriched program containing full-grown activity patterns.

Layer Cake – (researcher's &) student's design process

During this phase, students were asked to develop the experiential content of their spatial layer, with the help of the theoretical information we had provided them with.

During the first two days of designing social scenarios, we noticed that the role of the first author was important in order to co-work with students to develop methods to combine their chosen topic and the 'psychological information' of the building blocks into architectural designing. To start with, the first author stimulated students to think out narratives: social stories and logical activity patterns that could occur within their chosen social topic. Each time, examples were given in what way the building blocks could help students to come up with these scenarios, and stay focused on the target group's needs. For example, the design group working around the topic 'spending time outdoors' (project "Tussen de soep en de patatten") were stimulated to develop garden activities that allowed residents to pick up on their hobby of gardening (to fulfil building blocks 'execute hobbies' and 'train & master existing skills', and even 'mindfulness'), invent scenarios with cooking workshops that allowed residents to maintain or gain extra skills regarding preparing food (to fulfil building blocks 'train & master existing skills', 'develop new skills' and even 'engage in meaningful activities'), but could also lead to fulfilling building block 'reminiscence' when preparing long lost recipes and picking up on the aroma of home-made soup, or to fulfilment of 'volunteering and charity' and 'solidarity & empathy', when a sort of soup kitchen is established. During these first attempts of designing scenarios, it became clear that most of the design groups tried to 'manage' the design challenge by subcategorizing their chosen topic. For instance the group whose social topic was 'sports', made the subdivision of 'active', 'semi-active' and 'passive' ways of practising sports. The group whose social topic was 'spending time outdoors' even made two types of subdivisions: (1) activities in each of the four seasons and (2) three additional themes they further wanted to explore in their design: 'vegetable garden', 'soup bar' and 'relaxing outdoors'. This was an important first step in concretizing their topic and simultaneously linking it even more to the lifestyle of elderly persons, since the inspiration for categorization came from rereading the narratives that they collected at the

Figure 3. Flow of activities.

Figure 4. Spider web of activities.

start of the master class. After subcategorizing, it became easier for students to develop scenarios related to their social topic, and finding matches between the scenarios and the building blocks in the framework.

We call this step in the design process ‘concretizing social concept’, see Figure 6.

The next days, the first author encouraged students to elaborate the scenarios they had already designed, by (1) iteratively trying to include as many building blocks as possible in the story and expanding their designed new narratives, (2) exploring links between different scenarios, (3) finding ramifications in the scenario, meaning that one action might lead to a number of possible other actions, and (4) making sure that every type of elderly person is ‘included’ in the scenarios, by layering activities in intensity, duration and frequency (Fogg, 2009). At that moment, we noticed that students further developed the scenarios in two manners: starting out from the user (the different types of elderly persons (target group) and outsiders) or from the subthemes and categorizations within their social topic. For instance in the design project of the social topic ‘library’, the design group drew a flow chart per type of user that they had defined in their design process (i.e., a fit resident of Layer Cake, a resident with dementia disorder and the grandson of a resident), and developed a scenario that included many actions and activities with this user as a protagonist, and other people included. The building blocks were applied in this process to design activities that have a specific aimed effect on the predefined user(s). This approach led to the development of a *flow of activities*; one activity set others in motion, and an overlap between the scenarios arose. By repeating this process many times, and trying to fulfil as many building blocks as possible, a coherent story for the usage patterns of the library was developed and a logical sequence of activities and events was presented, see an example in Figure 3.

Most of the design groups started out from the subthemes they had developed for their social topic. For instance the group working with the topic ‘sports’ had come up with two types of subcategorizations: four different sport zones (yoga & dance, mini golf, running, and active sport such as biking) and three

different perspectives on and intensities of sports related to a specific user group (a resident’s kin, a resident that likes recreational sports, a resident in need of physical rehabilitation). In developing their scenarios, specifically for each of the four zones, they first filled in a framework of building blocks with suitable activities. Concretely, they ran through each of the 17 building blocks to define events that could be undertaken. Then, per zone, they coded their activities with regards to the three different types of user groups they had defined earlier. In that way, the activities became even more layered and detailed regarding the zone they were in, and the specifics and characteristics of the different user groups. That way of working led to a web of many different empowering events that can occur for all different users within the four zones. Also, by each designed addition, the activities became more socially layered and detailed in flourishing effect. So that way of designing led to an elaborate mix of activities, or in other words a spider web of activities within the imaginary boundaries of the social topic, as illustrated in Figure 4.

We labelled this step in the design process ‘scenario development, enriched program’, see Figure 6.

With the end of the first design week approaching, students were asked to continue and keep on elaborating the scenarios they had designed, by including more possible users, searching for more overlaps between the activities or including more building blocks within the story told. This became an iterative process of thinking out scenarios and immediately evaluating them by (re)running them through the framework of building blocks, with all the different members of the target group in mind. Each time another type of person entered a scenario, the framework was reapplied to argue what behaviour could be provoked and in what way that person could be assisted in flourishing in the already designed scenarios, or what new scenarios had to be written. Also, when non-residents (visitors, neighbours, passers-by) entered the scenarios, the framework was of use to see in what way these people could benefit each other and residents. Consequently, programs of usage became even more enriched and layered in flourishing experiences, and an overall picture of the daily goings in each spatial layer in Layer Cake became clear. Then, the socio-cultural affordances were designed, and the first part of a DfHF-process is ran through, see Figure 1.

Visualization

Throughout the first design week, students had to daily communicate their designed social scenarios to the first author and guest studio mentors. Hence, attention to finding suitable ways of visually communicating the complex social designs was on the students’ to do list as well.

When analysing students’ ways of representation at the jury that concluded the first design week, we noticed differences in visualisation methods used by the design groups that had designed their enriched program starting out from developed subcategories within their social topic, and the groups that had

Figure 5. Representations to communicate designed socio-cultural affordances.

started from the users. As the left part of Figure 5 demonstrates, a visual representation of the framework of building blocks, added with collages and 3D images per scenario was the most important output of design groups that had started out from their subcategories. Design groups that had started from the user mostly applied flow charts and puzzle pictures, see the right part of Figure 5.

Conclusion: programmatic writing as a method to design socio-cultural affordances in a DfHF-process

As a conclusion, in Figure 6, all of the described design steps thoroughly discussed in this paper are generalized into a timeline visualizing the design process of socio-cultural affordances. In the top part of the time line, per yellow dot, the design steps are explained. The black dotted arrows, explain what kind of information or tips were inserted in the design process and by whom.

We label this design method “programmatic writing”. Concretely, programmatic writing is a mix of consecutive steps a designer needs to run through in order to develop an *enriched program*, which is key in HF-architecture. An enriched program exists of activity patterns and scenarios that comply with the psychological needs of the target group. When executed, the activities will assist these persons in flourishing. Those activities concern what we have labelled the so-called “socio-cultural affordances” of space.

By consciously using the verb “writing” in the naming of our design method programmatic writing, we stress that we focus on intangible programmatic features that need to be ‘designed’ and need particular attention in the early design phase, whereby we need to take into account that traditional work approaches such as sketching and drawing are not directly applicable in the early steps of programmatic writing. The program for a target group has to literally be thought out, and written out to make it graspable. Only in the final steps of programmatic writing, the designed scenarios are to be visualized by drawn schemes or collages as presented in Figure 5. Even then, the visualizations are from a different order than the floor-plan-sketches or 3D-images an architect traditionally produces when designing (e.g. Pena, 2001; Cross, 2011). To conclude, in contrast to traditional design methods, there is a prolonged and very intense design time spent on the intangible aspects of

architecture, namely the program with its activities as socio-cultural affordances, instead of jumping rather quickly into actual spatial designs that contain tangible information such as form, structure and material information (Cross, 2011).

Now that the method of programmatic writing is discussed, we can insert these insights into the theoretical trajectory for DfHF. In Figure 7, we have repeated the theoretical trajectory, and uploaded the socio-cultural affordance-part with the details and techniques of the developed design method of programmatic writing. The process starts by collecting experiential and psychological information from the target group. A close contact and empathic connection with this target group is requested. Next, the design process continues with designing enriched social programs. Thinking out narratives (storytelling) and scenario writing are important techniques that architects can use to design meaningful activities out of the psychological data that are collected from their target group. We believe that designing these social scenarios on different architectural scale levels is a way of integrating very complex demands of heterogenic target groups in a manageable way. Scenarios can be combined, placed next to each other to find interesting overlaps, points of conflict or opportunities. Note that in order to DfHF, architects must still translate the socio-cultural affordances into physical affordances. In further research, we aim to theoretically and designerly explore methods to do so.

Discussion, implications & further research

In this paper we discussed the design method of “programmatic writing” that was developed during the design exercise Layer Cake, with the purpose of introducing it as a way to design socio-cultural affordances in a DfHF-process. It is a first attempt in transforming DfHF-theory into a practical tool to steer architects. The design exercise with students made clear that a mentality shift needs to occur during designing, since spatial designers have the intention to direct their attention towards sketching and drawing spatial ‘solutions’ (Pena, 2001; Cross, 2011). However in DfHF, intangible aspects need to be handled in detail before the actual spatial decisions can be made. Therefore, during the exercise, the first author stressed the importance of using the framework of the building blocks, thinking in terms of scenarios and telling stories to each other; and somewhat ‘forbid’ the students in the first design week to speak in spatial terms and jump to spatial

Figure 6. Design process of socio-cultural affordances: the method of programmatic writing.

Socio-cultural affordance:
Meaningful, rich experiences

Figure 7. Programmatic writing inserted in the theoretical trajectory to DfHF in architecture.

conclusions. On the other hand, 'spatial' expectations of the users need to be met when a design is presented to them. Therefore, in DfHF, architects must find suitable ways to concretize their designed socio-cultural affordances into a more 'tangible' way of presentation than simply verbal communication. This implies that designers need to experiment with communication tools of sketching and drawing to get the message across and convince with their designed efforts and the experiences the design will provide.

With programmatic writing as a possible design method to design socio-cultural affordances, an important step in concretizing this trajectory is set. This has implications for architectural practice, since designers are in need of explicit information on how to DfHF, and place the experiential world of the user first. However, more research is necessary to explore how this method can work in actual design practice and what possible pitfalls designers can encounter; truly getting to know the target group and investing design time in developing an enriched program prolongs the design process, which has financial consequences for firm and client, an issue that cannot be neglected in the context of professional design activities. Also, DfHF requests a mind-shift of the designer, so it is our responsibility to research in what way we can assist the designer to overcome difficulties in that matter, and develop the design tool in a way that it is easy to apply for designers, and presented to them in the visual language they are familiar with.

If the trajectory is found to be useful and applicable in practice, we believe it is relevant for many architectural contexts such as care typologies or school environments, in short, places where people need to reside for a specific period of time. If patients in care environments and children in school environments feel well and are flourishing, this might have a positive influence on their healing or study performance as well. Thereby we aim to reach a large number of the population. DfHF positively influences the psychological well-being of people, and we can thereby contribute to the Gross National Happiness of nations (The Centre for Bhutan Studies & GNH Research, 2015).

In future research, we will investigate in what way architecture with a more humane undertone implicitly works with the three components in the trajectory. Also, we aim to set up a similar research path to designerly explore physical affordances as well (see Figure 1), and by that complete a DfHF-trajectory for architects and interior architects from an affordance perspective. However, we believe that this new way of designing can be extrapolated to other design branches, such as industrial design, etcetera. Design methods will logically differ from the architectural ones, so more research is necessary in that respect.

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Video-mediated participation in virtual museum tours for older adults

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Abstract This paper introduces a virtual tour, *Visit the Louvre*, designed specifically to engage older adults in an immersive visit through part of the Louvre by a distant real-life guide. An initial diary study and a creative workshop were conducted to understand the needs and values of older adults and how to support participation to virtual museum visits with a video-based communication system. Preliminary results show that ‘virtual visitors’ experienced high levels of social and spatial presence; immersion and engagement were quite high independent of the level of interactivity of the guide, or the presence of others.

Keywords *Older adults, Museum, Virtual visit, Social inclusion, Civic participation*

Introduction

The number of older adults is growing fast. Cognitive decline, physical isolation and lack of transportation can limit the ability of older adults to move around and to participate in public life as they did before (Winsted et. al, 2013; Berkowsky et. al, 2013; Cotton, 2012). Social connections can be lost due to retirements, relocation or widowhood. Engagement in social activities can be restricted by illness, physical and cognitive decline and mobility problems. Contact with friends and family is important for perceived social support (Wherton and Prendergast, 2009).

The Internet has the potential to enhance social connections and communication in a variety of ways. Recent studies show that information and communication technologies (ICT) can help older adults overcome social and spatial barriers (Winsted et. al, 2013; Berkowsky et. al, 2013; Cotton, 2012). In essence, the use of ICTs is seen as a means for older adults to ‘reconnect or improve their connection with the outside world’ (Selwyn, 2003). Previous research has shown that social support and the use of communication technologies can lower perceived life stress (Wright, 2000), and improve psychosocial well-being among older adults (White et. al, 1999).

Older adults are reported to have a stronger sense of social inclusion when they spend more time on using the Internet, as according to Nahm et al. (2003) they often have a larger social computer-mediated network and in turn, levels of connectedness. Mason et al. (2012) reported that older adults in assisted and

independent living communities that used Internet, showed reduced levels of loneliness and increased social contacts. Using the Internet and technology as a means for communication may allow older adults to compensate for potential mobility loss and lifestyle changes associated with ageing. Winstead et al. (2013) reports on qualitative studies where older adults from assisted living communities used technology like Google Maps with Street View and virtual tours to “visit” places of interest that are no longer accessible to them. These online visits resulted in lower levels of loneliness and social isolation.

How older adults communicate online may also impact on their sense of social inclusion and social connectedness. According to media richness theory, the richer the communication medium is (in terms of social cues) the more effective the communication is (Kock, 2005). When communicating face-to-face, individuals are able to use words, vocal cues, and non-verbal behavior in order to communicate factual and social information in a fast and unambiguous manner (Dennis and Kinney, 1998). Therefore, a communication with video would be more ‘natural’ than an only audio communication. Moreover, video-mediated communication (VMC) systems have developed further and now present a rich form of communication (Bohannon, 2013) and a live window between remote spaces. Conventional VMC systems (like Skype) typically support users who want to interact in a face-to-face manner, but do not provide a seamless mediated space for social contact and shared activities. Although possible with current

Figure 1. An impression of SharedSpaces: Each user is positioned in front of a green cloth (a) and users from different location are shown together in the same space by merging their independent video streams (b). Users can draw together (c) and or can change the backdrop (d).

technologies, there are very few communication platforms that facilitate creative interaction at a distance (Hunter, 2014).

This paper describes the development of a new video-based communication system designed to support older adults in visiting a museum without having to leave their homes. Different methods were used to elicit information from potential users at each step of the design process. These methods were instrumental in developing the concept, establishing requirements and creating the virtual tour. We report on the design process, as well as on the results of a preliminary user test in which we studied how older adults experienced the designed communication.

System overview

SharedSpaces is a design prototype from the EU-funded FP7 project COMPEIT (Gullström, 2014). It was used as the basis for the video-based communication system we designed. SharedSpaces invites users from multiple locations to interact and seamlessly move between different real and virtual spaces by integrating separated media channels. It supports social dynamics, by allowing users to move and resize their real-time video streams, or to draw and paint together. It enhances the feeling of being in the same space, by representing users side by side in a shared virtual space.

Design process

The design process consisted of three main phases. First, a diary study was conducted to understand the problems being addressed, and to understand the social circles of older adults and places older adults would like to visit. Second, a creative facilitation session took place in which data from the diary study were fed to a team of design students, to identify opportunities for the SharedSpaces technology. These ideas were then discussed and 6 unified concepts were proposed. The third phase was a user study involving 8 older adults to establish design requirements and guidelines for good interaction practices within the SharedSpaces environment. In this section we describe each phase and highlight the main outcomes that guided the development of our system.

Diary study

In order to understand the values of our users, and to better inform the design process, we performed a diary study. The aim was to:

- Understand the social networks of older adults and how social relationships are supported as of today;
- Understand the role of places they visit and their effect on social relationships;
- Understand the role of ICT and their role in supporting social relationships and activities.

The design of the diary study was based on a method already developed and implemented for the needs of the COMPEIT project, where the values and needs for children as a target group for COMPEIT were investigated (Kort et. al., 2014). In the diary study, older adults were asked to fill out diaries for one week. The participants kept track of:

- people they see from their social network (Figure 2);
- places they visit (Figure 3) and;
- ICT and social media they use;
- their activities (including with whom, where and why), and whether any technology was used.

The aim of the diary study was to help the researchers better understand older adults and their behaviors (activities), goals, attitudes, as well as to identify the opportunities these provide for further designing and developing SharedSpaces solutions. Specifically, it focused on obtaining detailed insights into how older adults experience daily activities and communication with others, in combination with specific places that are important to them or that play a particular role in their lives. Next to keeping a diary on a daily basis for one week, we aimed to obtain insights in specific places, as well as in the group of people they would like to stay in touch with. Many of these assignments were based on storytelling and creative thinking (tell us how you liked a specific situation; how would you deal with it differently). Questions included:

What are the most fun and least fun things you did today and what made them fun or least fun? Can you think of two examples of two places you would like to

Figure 2. Social network page of the diary: participants fill in which people fit in which circle: family and best friends (1), people that I now and then meet (3). Designed by Bart! Grafisch ontwerp © UX Tools.

Figure 3. Places older adults visit: page in the diary where participants fill in places they visit often (1), regularly (2) and sometimes (3). Designed by Bart! Grafisch ontwerp © UX Tools.

connect to with a magic door and can you tell us why you want to connect to these places? Imagine you have a set of flying ears and eyes, where would you send them and why? If you had a machine that could take you anywhere, where would you go and with whom?

A total of 10 diary booklets were distributed via the social networks of the researchers. Five booklets were returned. Older adults that returned a fully filled out booklet received a voucher of 20,- euros. It was mandatory to sign a consent form stating they were informed about the research, and in which they acknowledged their participation.

Results from the diary study

Social networks of older adults. The inner social circle includes: sister(s), brother(s), partner(s), son(s), daughter(s), sister(s) in law, brother(s) in law. The middle circle (friends and people I often see or talk to, I am related to but not in the same way or as close as to the people in my inner circle) include: partners of the kids, friends, acquaintances through hobbies. The outer circle (people with whom I have contact every now and then) include: neighbors, old colleagues, ex classmates.

Places older adults visit. Places they often visit include: town, balcony, garden, friends' or brothers' or sisters' home, tennis club. Places they visit regularly include: sister or brother in law, aunts, friends. Places they sometimes visit include: daughter, grandchildren, and friends.

Technologies they use. Technologies for staying in touch: Facebook, Telephone, Google+, Facebook Messenger, Twitter, Skype. Technologies for pleasure: TV.

Examples of daily activity entries. Most common activities included: preparing and having breakfast, reading newspaper(s), preparing and having lunch, grocery shopping, staying in touch with family members, watching TV, preparing and having dinner,

participating in cultural events or hobbies (tennis club) and having visits from the kids usually on weekends.

Most and least fun thing of the day. Among the most fun things that our participants did were: drinking tea with a friend, playing games on iPad, playing chess, cooking, organizing photos. When asked what made these fun, the participants provided the following reasons: because it was cozy and it is a pleasure to perform the activities, or in the case of playing games because they won the game. Among the least fun things participants mentioned: partner being sick, or mail that brings bad news, or not feeling good. On the questions what made them least fun participants responded that in the case when the partner or they were not feeling good, that they could not move around.

If they could connect two different places with a door, which places would they connect? Participants proposed different places to be connected, some of the ideas were: connecting the house to an island, Bali, coast, and places where kids live. Types of activities they want to perform when they would go to beach/island/coast: walk, seat and read, listening to the waves, relax, ride a bike. In the case of connecting the house with the places where kids live: to catch up with people, drink coffee, be together with them.

If they would have pairs of 'flying eyes and ears' where would they send them? Participants expressed the desire to see grandchildren in order to see how they are doing, or brother and sister in law, and family members in general for the same reason.

If there's a machine that could take them and people they care about to any place, where would that be, and who would they take with them? Participants would like to go to visit a museum, or somewhere to eat or drink something. Some participants wanted to go to events where authors speak about books and sign books later. Also participants expressed a preference of walking

through the streets of unknown cities and admiring the architecture.

Reflections. Some participants reflected that when one gets older and sick the amount of friends is getting smaller; to go out is really important. The telephone and iPad are important to be and stay in touch. Some reflected that having family and close friends is really important and that they enjoy quality time with them.

Creative facilitation

The second phase focused on identifying technological opportunities from the material collected through the diary studies, in order to establish a design concept. We conducted a creative facilitation session, to translate the user insights into design ideas and conceptual designs for scenarios of using SharedSpaces that would match the user insights, in order to then select one scenario to further develop within the project. The creative facilitation session took place inside TU Delft, on Sept 18th 2015. The group consisted of 6 design students. The session lasted 4 hours and participants were paid 10 euros for their participation. Participants were asked to come up with ideas that would encourage and support older people to collaborate over a distance using SharedSpaces. The results from the diary study, as well as the possibilities of the SharedSpaces prototype were given as input for the session. The session resulted in the 6 different design concepts discussed below.

Sightseeing: A guide gives a tour of a city while the older adults see it and participate in the tour, live from home. For example, the guide can show the Eiffel tower or the Louvre in real time. Older adult can also attend a conference.

Get together: The family goes on a biking trip, the older adult joins from home on static bike. One family member is equipped with a camera on the bike and the older adult at home sees the stream and is projected in the video of the family.

Recipe sharing at distance: An experienced older adult cook gives an online lesson and guides a cooking session. All other participants are close to the cook, see the cook and learn how to cook from the older adult cook.

Virtual waiting room and virtual medical examination:

The older adult can go for a medical visit from home. The older adult waits in a waiting room together with other older adults that wait for a medical visit.

The crafting room: The older adults give a tutorial for knitting, the participants are interested young adults that want to learn how to knit.

Let's discuss: People participate in political gatherings in public spaces (squares) through big screens where they are projected in the crowd.

The design opportunities were reviewed afterwards. Some of the ideas were presented in the form of a

storyboard, which included 4 to 6 frames depicting the solution.

Afterwards, we decided to proceed with the **Sightseeing** concept because of our background and knowledge of the domain. As the setting in the SharedSpaces prototype, we chose a virtual representation of a room inside the Louvre and implemented an approach based on storytelling. Enriching visits through storytelling is a proven practice for museums: it both educates and entertains and provides a more engaging, adaptive and fundamentally enjoyable visitor experience (Giaccardi, 2006; and Wyman et al., 2011). In order to develop the tour we followed the storytelling suggestions presented in (Pujol et al., 2013).

We envisioned a solution as realistic as possible and in which people would thus stand while they participate. In our scenario, the guide meets the participants at the meeting point in the virtual room, and brings them to the presented statues one by one, by changing the background to a zoomed in presentation of the statue of interest (see Figure 4 (c) and (d)). Participants interact with the guide while having the possibility to point to the detail of interest and ask additional questions.

User study

As a third step, we performed a small-scale study in a research lab in order to understand how the participants would experience the concept. One guide (in our case a researcher) was involved in the experiment. We studied:

1. *interaction techniques:* the guide gives either a *free exploration tour* i.e. the guide does not require any further participation by the participants and participants interact only upon their own request, or *guided participatory tour* where the guide asks the participants for collaboration at certain points of the tour;
2. *group size:* the participant does the visit alone (only with the guide) or two participants do the visit together at the same time (from two different locations, both accompanied by the guide)

The study was conducted inside the Usability lab, in TNO, Groningen and inside TU Delft University, the experimental setup is shown in Figure 4 (a) and (b).

Once the participants understood how to use the tool, they were guided in a visit of the five exhibited statues (Figure 4 (c)), one after each other (Figure 4 (d)). In the free exploration tour the guide was just showing the statues, telling more information about the story behind them. In the beginning of this setting, the participants were welcomed to interrupt the guide in the tour and ask questions if they had any additional questions about the content. In the guided participatory tour the guide triggered a small reflection talk or a small collaboration task about the content after each presented object. After the experiment participants were presented with a questionnaire and the personal opinions of the participants were discussed in semi-structured

Figure 4. The look of the stations used for testing (a) and (b), the Rotonde Hall, place where the guide initially meets the participant(s) (c) and a closer look at one of the exhibited statues (d).

interviews at the end of the session.

We used a validated questionnaire created in previous research for measuring the constructs of social, spatial presence, immersion, engagement and naturalness (Kort et. al, 2010). The questionnaire contains 13 items, each item is a statement, and we invited participants to state the level up to which they agree or disagree with the statement on a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 = “totally disagree” and 5 = “totally agree”. During the experiment, the researcher was taking observation notes on the predefined observation sheet. The researcher took additional observation notes immediately after the experiment, when the participants were filling in the questionnaire. In the semi-structured interview in the end, we discussed with participants what they liked, what they would like to see different, and what problems they encountered.

We recruited 8 older participants for the study, through word of mouth (5 males and 3 females). Five participants reported prior use of communication technologies like Skype or Google Hangouts. The participants again received a 20,- euro voucher for their participation. We had 4 participants participating in groups of 2 (and the guide), and 4 participants participating alone with the guide. One of the groups followed the guided participatory tour, while the other followed the free exploration tour. Two

Table 1. Overview of participants and variants.

	Free exploration tour	Guided participatory tour
Individual	P3 and P4	P5 and P6
In pairs	P1 paired with P2	P7 paired with P8

of the individual participants followed the guided participatory tour and two followed the free exploration one (Table 1).

Results of questionnaire

Mean experience assessment of presence was 3.91 (SD = .76), immersion and engagement 4.29 (SD = .80), and naturalness 3.91 (SD = .88) (Figure 5). We conclude that participants felt presence, naturalness, and immersion and engagement. Because of the small numbers of participants we decided to pursue a qualitative approach for analyzing possible differences between conditions. We didn't observe any noticeable effects of the freedom of interaction on constructs; participants across both conditions (free exploratory or guided participatory) commented that they felt as if they were in the same space. Also, we didn't observe any particular effect of the number of people participating in the tour.

Insights from the interview

Participants in the test commented on various issues around the virtual visit. They discussed how they experienced the virtual visit as compared to a real visit, the role of a guide, the duration and interestingness of the tour and they provided suggestions for tailoring the tour. We frame the discussion in form of guidelines for future designers/ researchers developing similar interventions.

Virtual visit versus real visit. Our system allowed older adults to not be bothered by crowds around objects (as they would in real museums), which sometimes can be experienced as too tiring. In this way visiting exhibitions and museums in general can

Figure 5. The means and the standard deviations of the constructs.

become more enjoyable and cozy. To visit the museum from home, without having to leave your own seat was found really appealing. One of the participant commented:

"In a real museum they write all the information on a plate near the object and you stand close to the plate and you have to read. In this scenario, you visit from home, and someone tells you all this information. Additionally, you can consult on Wikipedia immediately if something seems really interesting."

Some participants commented that this approach is more suited for seeing paintings and other more 2D objects. The participants encountered problems with trying to point out to some specific parts of the statues in the room.

Role of the guide. One of the participants that recently traveled to Israel, commented:

"The first day I walked without a guide. It was such a waste of time to walk around and not to understand all the important things that I was surrounded with. The second day I joined a guided tour and I realized that the previous day I passed next to a place where the hand of Jesus was placed and I didn't even know! Having the person to point out the details is important, otherwise it is really easy to miss important information."

Participants commented that in busy places as museum one can easily miss an important object just because one doesn't know that it is an important object. Having a guide helps, because you are sure that you get to know all the important things.

Duration and interestingness of the tour. Some participants found the topic of the exhibition interesting and some said that it did not fit their interests in general. Some of the participants showed additional curiosity and asked to have the names of the statues and asked the presented content to be sent by email, so they could inform themselves more from home. Mostly, they found the duration of the explanation quite adequate for the purpose: *"I think for me it was just the right amount of information, not too much not too less"*

Suggestions on the general tour level. Some participants commented that in a huge museum like the Louvre there won't be stories behind each presented statue. They proposed to have a longer

version of the tour, uniting more statues, connecting them across similar themes. Additionally they suggested to have the approach tailored for kids, commenting: *"Kids like scary stories"*

They commented that it would be nice if one can discuss before and agree with the guide what kind of tour to have. Different people can have interests in different type of information about the content: more details about the style and materials, the story behind it, or more information about the author. Participants also asked for a more connected approach: to highlight the connection between objects in museum, and to connect different arts on the same topic (poems, paintings, music inspired by the same theme). They proposed to present information across 4 dimensions: content of the object, context (historical and physical), the artist details, and technique. We believe that if incorporated, these presentation aspects can significantly influence the level engagement and immersion.

Observing interactions. Different patterns of interactions between participants or with the setup emerged in the sessions. Some of the people were negotiating their positions between themselves or/and the guide in the way that it leaves space for the statue to be seen. Some other participants were less sensitive to the change in the background and did not try to adjust, so the guide was supposed to specifically point out that there's a statue just behind them.

In one of the group sessions (with two participants at the same time) the room became too crowded since the participants were quite corpulent. This left no space for the participants to see the objects. The involved participants tried to move behind each other, but since the videos are overlapping it was difficult to find the right position as the person positioned behind another person was disappearing from the scene and tried to reach out from behind the person, which didn't always feel comfortable. Providing the right spatial affordance proved to be an important factor influencing the experience.

Lessons learned and conclusion

We developed a video-mediated communication tool that allows older adults, suffering from mobility loss, to visit a museum with a real guide. The guide takes the visitors along the sculptures whilst presenting small stories about them. Our participants in the user study found the tour appealing and interesting. The stories provided an additional meaning to the presented content and it immersed participants into the subject. We believe that stories were important for subject's immersion. Participants in general talked with the guide and talked on topic of the exhibition. Many of them tried to reach out and point to specific details of the presented content. The experienced levels of presence, immersion and engagement and naturalness were rather high, which showed us that we are on the right track. Differences in experience between the conditions (interaction technique and group size) as measured by the questionnaire were not found. A wider sample of participants may be needed to further explore possible effects of the conditions.

We understood that we can significantly improve the approach if the guide can discuss beforehand with the participants and tailor the tour based on the interest of the participants according on the following dimensions: content about the object, historical and physical context around the object, the artist details, and technique. The sense of orientation could be improved by having a video stream that is not mirrored. Future design research could focus on exploring how the approach can be made to accommodate differences in interest between participants, as well as on verifying whether not-mirroring the video stream is a solution to the loss of orientation that sometimes occurred in pointing to the displayed objects.

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Product experience and luxury values

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Abstract Designing for luxury is a challenge since it requires knowledge on the concept of luxury and how to transfer this knowledge to product design. Literature on the concept of luxury offers a variety of definitions of the term and discusses the role and meaning of luxury by referring to particular disciplines such as economics, sociology and marketing. These studies occasionally touch upon aspects that are associated with luxury products; however there is no specific research that provides guidelines or frameworks to support designers in luxury product development. This study argues that luxury values found across the literature can contribute to defining dimensions of luxury product experience. Presenting the historical background and the definitions of the term 'luxury', this paper explores four different types of luxury values through product examples, and discusses relationships amongst these values. The findings point out a need to study luxury values within different aspects of product design, which can extend the current understanding beyond materialization and into the realms of user-product interaction, design and technology relationships, and design for experience.

Keywords *Luxury, Luxury values, Design for luxury, Product design, User experience*

Introduction

Luxury is a concept that is studied greatly in marketing but not deeply discussed in relation to product design. Existing luxury studies give clues about the communication of luxury through particular consumption phases and offer criteria for how to satisfy consumers of luxury goods. However, they fall short of information about design considerations that can lead to luxury experience through product usage. Similarly, many concepts and brands associated with luxury offer no specific guideline to assess the luxuriousness of their offerings. We need to know more about what it takes to create a luxury experience in products, interactions, and services. Therefore, this paper presents definitions of luxury that have evolved over time, which are then used as a basis to analyse contemporary literature on 'luxury values' together with product examples. The paper provides an understanding of the dimensions of luxury products and points out new research opportunities in the area of 'design for luxury product experience'.

The concept of luxury

Luxury is mostly associated with images of rich and powerful people but it is not easy to reach a universal or concrete definition. It is essentially a relative term (Mehta, 2014). For example, a particular car might be luxury to some people, whilst ordinary to others. In this regard, Kapferer (2012) points out the relativity of luxury by using the definition "the ordinary of the extraordinary".

Etymologically, the word luxury derived from the French term 'luxurie', which means "excess, lasciviousness, and negative self-indulgence". It can be further connected to the Latin word 'luxus', meaning

"soft or extravagant living, sumptuousness, opulence" (Oxford Dictionaries of English, 2015). However, these negative connotations tended to be replaced with positive associations with the Latin root 'lux' (i.e. light), referring to high-value objects made from optically bright and glossy precious materials (e.g. gold) to be used notably by royalty and the church (Brun & Castelli, 2013).

In the Oxford Dictionaries of English (2015) the definitions of luxury are provided as "a state of great comfort or elegance, especially when involving great expense"; "an inessential, desirable item which is expensive or difficult to obtain" and "a pleasure obtained only rarely".

Depending on the context, luxury has been associated with superior qualities of an object or service, high price, high-class, rarity/uniqueness of a particular item, pleasurable experience, as well as unnecessary consumption and extravagant life-styles. Associations with quality tend towards a positive meaning of luxury, whereas associations with opulence tend towards a negative meaning. Throughout history, definitions and the scope of luxury have changed with milestones in sociology, economics and technology. As historical milestones affecting social changes and people's ways of living have been reached, so the concept of luxury has evolved and been redefined. In the ancient world, luxury was seen through buildings symbolizing wealth and power, whilst luxury items were presented as tributes to god(s) (Kapferer, 2012). However, indulgence in individualistic, excessive pleasures was not accepted as a virtue. In early industrial times, trade opportunities led society and individuals to become generally wealthier, making

luxury accessible to a larger and more diverse population. Later in the eighteenth century, society faced major events including liberalisation, democratisation, and women's rights movements, followed by the industrial revolution. In combination, these events brought a considerable rise in the living standards of middle and upper classes and contributed to luxury becoming more affordable to a wider populous (Kapferer & Bastien, 2009). Today, with shared changes in social life such as increased income, delayed marriage, and smaller families, people have more discretionary income to spend on their own luxuries (Silverstein & Fiske, 2003). Accordingly this brings into focus the relativity of the term luxury, since every social class can have their 'own kind' of luxuries.

Emergence of luxury brands

As luxury has strong connections with consumption, the positive and negative connotations of luxury have inevitably evolved with economic developments. The emergence of an industry or 'market segment' for luxury goods and luxury brands draws back to the nineteenth century's industrial revolution and the establishment of companies seeking to produce exceptional products for the taste of the social elite at that time (Antoni et al., 2004). High volume industrial production of luxury goods versus relatively slow local economic growth led to increasing emphasis on export sales to reach customers in other countries, which is reflected in the global operation basis of many of today's luxury companies (Antoni et al., 2004). Through the growth of business in the twentieth century, these companies broadened their customer base and earned a universal reputation for their "superior quality, durability, performance and design" (Brun & Castelli, 2013). Nowadays, the brand identity of such companies is in itself a symbol of luxury. In other words, although the quality of the product or offering is still vital, the concept of luxury has become increasingly bounded within marketing and brand communication.

So what makes certain brands or products 'luxury'? Adam Smith (1776) refers to luxury as "consumption of luxury products" and proposes the classification of consumption as: i) "necessary consumption to maintain life", ii) "basic consumption for normal growth and prosperity of people and communities", iii) "affluent consumption of goods that are not essential for growth and prosperity" and iv) "luxury consumption of goods that are in limited supply, difficult to procure and/or very expensive" (in Berthon et al., 2009).

Other sources in literature do not limit the concept of luxury to rare and very high priced products. For example, Kapferer (1997) suggests the qualities of a luxury brand as: "quality, beauty, sensuality, exclusivity, history, high price, and uniqueness". Whereas, Antoni et al. (2004) offer a list covering: "excellence, brand aura, and desirability". Reinmoller (2002) distinguishes luxury products from standard products by claiming that luxury products exceed the level of 'standard products' by "use of material, processes, packaging, distribution and promotion" to

provide "pleasure and indulgence". Brun and Castelli (2013) also investigated the constitution of luxury products and brands, and provided a more comprehensive list of answers, which they call "the critical success factors of luxury (CSF)" – proposed as a combination of selected definitions of luxury brands and products found in literature. Under CSF, a luxury product or brand should have the following aspects:

i) consistently delivering premium quality; ii) a heritage of craftsmanship; iii) emotional appeal (going beyond the technical specifications of a product); iv) global reputation of the brand; v) an association with a country of origin (e.g. 'Swiss' watches); vi) superior technical performance (e.g. luxury sports cars such as a Porsche Cayman); vii) elements that establish uniqueness/exclusivity (e.g. exclusivity generated by the specific manufacturing method, such as slightly uneven surfaces of mouth-blown glass vases); and, viii) "the creation of a lifestyle (e.g. the 'luxury of spontaneity' concept of Bentley Motors, which suggests particular routes in different continents to be explored by Continental GT customers) (Brun & Castelli, 2013).

Luxury values

In this paper, we explore the particular qualities or concepts (e.g. desirability, exclusivity, indulgence) that luxury brands and products are associated with. The intention is to lay foundations for a structured approach towards designing for luxury product experience, by first exposing the dimensions that define 'luxury' in the context of consumer products. These dimensions are discussed as 'luxury values'. Brands position themselves according to these luxury values, which also become incorporated into their design decision-making processes. Studies within the field of marketing – which has a direct link to product design – are found to focus on up to four main strands of luxury values, namely: 1) **financial value** (Wiedmann et al., 2013), 2) **functionality** (Reddy & Terblanche, 2005) or **functional value** (Berthon et al., 2009; Wiedmann et al., 2013), 3) **symbolic** (Berthon et al., 2009; Reddy & Terblanche, 2005) or **social value** (Wiedmann et al., 2013; Kapferer and Bastien, 2009), and 4) **experiential** (Berthon et al., 2009), **individual** (Wiedmann et al., 2013) or **personal value** (Kapferer & Bastien, 2009). These main strands are brought together in Figure 1.

In the following sections these values are discussed one by one and in relation to each other, with reference to product examples. In doing so, a better understanding of the relationship between product experience and luxury values is intended to be constructed.

Financial value

Financial value is directly related to the monetary worth of a product (Ahtola, 1984). Wiedmann et al. (2009) claim that financial value does not always have to reference the point-of-sale price, it can also refer to an investment value (e.g. an art object predicted to increase in financial value over time).

The retail price of a luxury product can be linked with

Figure 1. Four luxury values relevant to design.

Figure 2. Rolex Pearlmaster 39 (left), Richard Mille RM 027 (right).

several product features including valuable materials or embodied technologies. Oakley (2015) explains that some luxury watches obtain their high retail price from valuable gems, such as the Rolex Pearlmaster, whereas for other watches the high prices stems from high-technology processing of materials including carbon fibre and lithium titanium alloys, used for example in the Richard Mille RM 027 (Figure 2).

Functional value

Purchasers of non-luxury products of course expect that their purchases work properly. In the case of luxury products, the expectation is of 'perfect' functioning and service. This expectation overlaps with the core benefits that Wiedmann et al. (2013) lists: quality, uniqueness, usability, reliability, and

Figure 3. Bentayga SUV on the road (Bentley Motors, 2015).

durability. The core benefits are provided through design details that combine the highest quality materials, technology, engineering, etc. Reddy and Terblanche (2005) conclude that for some brands (e.g. Porsche), the value placed on technical superiority is a key brand attribute – thus the functional value of Porsche cars is a principle determinant of their luxuriousness. Berthon et al. (2009) state that every luxury brand has its material embodiment and the functional value is defined by how the brand's products perform and are experience in use in the material world, rather than what the product 'represents'.

Functional value is crucial to luxury car manufacturers, whose commercial success is based on superior performance and technical expertise. To illustrate, Bentley's 2015 Bentayga SUV (Sport Utility Vehicle) was released as the world's fastest SUV, with a top speed of 301kph (Figure 3). The vehicle is promoted by the company "with innovation at its heart, it displays unprecedented power, speed and efficiency, setting new standards in the SUV sector." (Bentley Motors, 2015).

Symbolic Value

Symbolic value can be defined as the creation of meanings through exposure to luxury brands, products or services. Symbolic value has two aspects: i) meaning created by a brand to symbolize its identity to society, and ii) socially constructed meaning that is assigned to the consumers of a particular brand by society. To exemplify, as Berthon et al. (2009) claim, "...a Ferrari may signal wealth, prestige, and performance, and it can be used to constitute and reinforce the owner's self-image as well."

Luxury brand identity is based on attributes including wealth, prestige, heritage, craftsmanship, superior quality, expertise, country of origin, uniqueness, etc. Different brands may place different emphasis on these attributes, and prefer different strategies in relation to their promotion. For example, Montblanc (predominantly known for its luxury pens and watches) constructs narratives based on its heritage of craftsmanship and explains this as: "creating an invisible bond between craftsmen's souls and their

Figure 4. Frederic Constant watch and fine manufacturing process in Geneva, Switzerland (Frederic Constant, 2015).

customers' soul" (Montblanc, 2015). On the other hand, Rolex chooses a different strategy, and associates its own brand with James Cameron's identity and lifestyle. They promote their superior quality by designing a showcase watch – the Rolex Deepsea Challenge model – to accompany James Cameron in "his journey to deepest place on earth" (2012). As another strategy, brands can emphasize connections and affinity to their country of origin. Kapferer and Bastien (2009) elaborate on this, claiming that a luxury product is a small fragmentation of the culture from which it is produced. Furthermore, a specific geographic location can play an important role in delivering exclusivity in a particular luxury product sector. For example, as with many Swiss watchmakers, Frédérique Constant operates within the watchmaking heritage of Geneva, which became known as a major centre for the creation and production of fine timepieces from the 18th century (Figure 4).

In an alternative approach, Chanel communicates its uniqueness through a set of icons, such as their logo (the intertwined C's), "little black dress", and the number five (Grigorian et al., 2014).

All of these strategies are examples for how symbolic value contributes to luxury brand perception. However, symbolic value can also be formed – as suggested by Reinmoeller (2002) – within social settings, through repeated interaction between people sharing similar interests and knowledge. Kapferer and Bastien (2009) also touch upon this, where membership of a particular group or community is reached through a common usage and ownership of luxury products – in other words, the concept of 'social luxury consumption'. In such instances, people use luxury brands to create a self-image, to present their wealth, prestige, au courant taste etc. to others, and to become conspicuous within social circles (Vigneron & Johnson, 2004).

Luxury brands transfer their symbolic value to society via promotion strategies (e.g. creating narratives, association with celebrities etc.) and make their brand recognizable by setting some exclusive features (e.g. icons, distinguished style and design). People can recognize these brands from their promotion strategies and exclusive features, and associate customers owning and using those branded products as being sympathetic to, and reflective of, the symbolic value communicated by the brand.

Figure 5. Montblanc M pen.

Experiential value

Experiential value is related with an individual person's experience with a luxury product. This experience involves "sensations, feelings, cognitions and behavioural responses" evoked by a specific "design and identity, packaging and communications" (Berthon et al., 2009, p.10).

Kapferer and Bastien (2009) discuss experiential value under their heading 'personal luxury consumption', implying that luxury consumption is for individual satisfaction. According to Wiedmann et al. (2013) individual satisfaction includes not only materialistic aspirations and hedonic motives but also the strengthening of a person's self-identity. Experiential value depends on the subjective taste of customers, and deals with the personal, hedonic value that is found in a brand (Berthon et al., 2009). For example, some Bang & Olufsen customers may choose to buy a loud speaker for the high fidelity sound it offers, whereas others may choose that particular speaker for its distinctive design and manufacturing details. Another example is a Montblanc M pen (Figure 5), offering noticeably different experiences in use, such as the iconic 'sound' of its cap, comfortable writing, and automatic alignment of the cap and the body – each of which will appeal in different measures to different customers.

Experiential value is not only about qualities embodied within a product, but also about the wider presentation and offering of a product. The design and ambience of the shop that a product is presented in, as well as the interaction with salespeople, can contribute to (or detract from) the feeling of luxury as a sense of refinement, contentedness and exclusiveness. Creation of experiential value by luxury product presentation is exemplified by Grigorian et al. (2014) with the Le Labo perfume experience. Le Labo offers a tailor-made experience to its customers by preparing perfumes in front of them. This ritual concludes with perfume bottles personalized with the customer's name (Figure 6).

Discussion

To this point, the paper has reviewed definitions of luxury, evolution of the meaning of luxury through time, the emergence of luxury brands, and the values that contribute to achieving a luxury experience from brands and products. Attention is now given to how those values are interconnected and how relationships between luxury values can be observed.

Figure 6. The Le Labo Perfume Experience.

Relationships between the four luxury values

To create a luxury experience, brands take all four values into account but may position themselves differently by concentrating on each value at a different level (Figure 7). For example a luxury car brand may promote a newly released car with its functional (high performance, durability) and financial (technology) value whereas a perfume company may emphasize more on individual (scent) and symbolic (iconic bottle, logo, scent etc.) value (Figure 7).

Whilst the four values have been explained individually in the paper, it is worth noting the possibility that the values may also influence each other, such as a particular value contributing to the creation of other values or one product property becoming associated with more than one value.

Financial value is regarded as having a significant effect on other values, since all the other values are the result of brand investment through money and time. These investments are reflected in the high retail price of luxury products. A brand can initially aim to create a product with a high financial value or it can prioritize other luxury values that will, over time, build a high financial value. The relationship between financial value and other values is presented as

follows.

- **Financial and functional value:** *Dubois et al. (2001) point out high price as the indicator and result of excellent quality. Functional value derives from a good combination of design, high quality materials, advanced technologies and engineering. All these aspects have an unavoidable financial cost due to time, access to expertise, investment in research and development, etc.*
- **Financial and symbolic value:** *High financial value makes a luxury product accessible only to a minority of people, which in turn converts that luxury product into a symbol of wealth. Vigneron and Johnson (2004) name this process as “conspicuous consumption”, which corresponds to having and using luxury brands as a means of social representation and status.*
- **Financial and experiential value:** *While making investments, luxury companies take into account all production and consumption phases ranging from iconic design development to end product advertisements, from the shopping experience to concierge. These investments enhance the experiential value but also come at a financial cost, which is inevitably passed on through high retail prices.*

Figure 7. Different products or brands show a distribution of emphasis across four luxury values.

If a product fails its function, it cannot offer quality tangible and social interactions. In this regard, symbolic and experiential values are valid or significant only so long as functional value is maintained. The effects of functional value on other luxury values can be summarised as follows.

- **Functional and experiential value:** *Products with high functional value help users to maintain their particular luxury lifestyle. For example, a luxury sports car (e.g. McLaren 570S) can offer such a grand tour travel experience that enables its users to explore long distances with exhilaration and adrenaline rushes thanks to its technical superiorities (quality materials and high performance).*
- **Functional and symbolic value:** *Using a luxury product with high functional value is the indicator of a refined taste that enhances one's self-representation within a social group. However, sometimes it is difficult to find a balance between functionality and symbolic value of a brand. For example, for most of the luxury brands that take their symbolic value from heritage or craftsmanship, it can be a challenge to successfully integrate advanced technologies.*

As all values are at some point intertwined, there is also a link between experiential and symbolic values. They might support or contradict each other depending on the context of luxury consumption.

- **Experiential and symbolic value:** *Symbolic value is related with what a luxury brand or product means to others, whereas experiential value is defined as the meaning to an individual (owner, user). There are some cases where a person's individual experience blends into their social experience as they share the appreciation of luxury product services. For example, luxury cars not only offer the pleasure of driving and the feel of a craftsman's touch through handmade interiors, but also the privilege of becoming a member of a 'select few' with a refined taste and means to indulge it. Nevertheless, experiential value and symbolic value can also manifest in a contrast, as in the example of wearing an uncomfortable shoe (low functional and experiential value) only because of what its brand represents (high symbolic value).*

Conclusions

This paper has provided a theoretical discussion on luxury values in relation to product experience. The review of literature on the concept of luxury revealed the existence of four main luxury values (functional value, financial value, symbolic value, and experiential value), which have tended to be discussed within the sphere of marketing. It is evident that luxury product features, luxury in use and luxury in relation to technology are all areas that have been overlooked in the literature and create opportunities for design research.

Previous studies have focused on how to create a luxury experience through marketing strategies rather than through luxury product features. There are some design concepts clearly associated with luxury (e.g.

quality, craftsmanship, multimodality) but how these concepts are reflected into and through product design is difficult to ascertain from literature. Therefore, this paper investigated the four luxury values in detail and discussed their relationships accompanied by product examples from different sectors. While referring to these examples, focus was given on those product features contributing to luxury experience, alongside promotion strategies that make a product appealing to a luxury market.

Another research opportunity for product design revealed by the paper is the need to understand how luxury is constructed through user-product interaction. Luxury is invariably seen as the combination of quality materials and technology, alongside specific production methods, but how luxury comes to light while users are interacting with products and information, beyond a materialization perspective, is an important design research question.

Finally, the traditional definition of luxury (e.g. heritage of craftsmanship, material combinations) challenges and is challenged by the application of advanced technologies. Especially in consumer electronics where such 'hi-tech' is adopted, it can be hard to maintain delivery of a luxury look and feel, at least in a traditional sense.

By exploring luxury values and product design, this paper has contributed to the identification of dimensions of luxury product experience that may be subsequently assembled within a framework of 'design for luxury'. In other words, the paper has provided an alternative approach to previous studies, which have tended not to be focused on product design considerations and their relationship to luxury values. In combination, the challenges and opportunities identified through the paper set a research agenda for better understanding of how to design for luxury experience with products.

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Happiness in place and space: Exploring the contribution of architecture and interior architecture to happiness

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Abstract Do architecture and interior architecture contribute to the happiness of people? Do these design disciplines have a role to play in enhancing possibilities for people to work on their happiness? To answer these questions, the first section of this paper discusses different factors that contribute to happiness: genetics, life circumstantial factors and intentional activities. Next, these factors are refined specifically from the viewpoint of architecture and interior architecture, whereby it is demonstrated how these disciplines can be considered as a life circumstantial factor that contributes to happiness. In the second section, a selection of techniques for exploring happiness and gaining insight in different factors contributing to happiness are discussed. Here, the authors discuss the set-up and use of a 'Happiness Circle', an exploratory tool which they developed in order to gain insight in the specific contribution that architecture and interior architecture can have regarding happiness. The results of an exploratory study wherein 212 research participants were involved demonstrate that architecture and interior architecture have a role to play in determining people's happiness, which opens various promising opportunities for future design projects.

Keywords *Happiness, Contribution of design, Happiness circle, Architecture, Interior architecture*

Introduction

'Happiness' or 'well-being' is one of the major, if not the ultimate goal, for every human being. Studying happiness is very important, relevant and timely because of several reasons. Firstly, there seems to be a societal need to focus on the well-being and happiness of people. In various industrial democracies, large groups of people continuously seem to have (had) the possibilities to fulfil their material needs and wants, and they start longing for other issues. Hence the growing interest of people to pay the necessary time, effort and attention to the fulfilment of immaterial aspects in life, their reappraisal of the search for and fulfilment of personal values, a good work-life balance, a healthy life etcetera. However, although people have the possibilities and the willingness to work on their well-being and happiness, research (Easterlin, 1974 ; Veenhoven, 1993) learns that measures of average happiness result in rather stationary data, in spite of people's increased possibilities. In academic literature, this phenomenon is known as the 'Easterlin Paradox' (Di Tella & MacCulloch, 2008). Secondly, from an economic point-of-view, paying attention to happiness seems highly relevant. Happy people seem to be successful in many domains of life, and these successes are at least in part due to their happiness. Happy people are more social, altruistic, and active, they like themselves more as well as others, they have healthy bodies and immune systems, and better conflict resolution skills. In addition, happiness seems to promote people's

capacity for constructive and creative thinking (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005b). These are all important issues and qualities of people that our industries and economies need today to face all kinds of challenges that lie ahead of us all. Thirdly, taking into account these perspectives, happiness has also become an issue on the political agenda. In 2011, the General Assembly of the United Nations accepted a resolution wherein they appealed to UN member states to undertake steps to give more attention to the pursuit of happiness of their citizens when determining how to achieve and measure social and economic development in their country (United Nations, 2011). In this respect, Bhutan is often a reference country: their 'Gross National Happiness Index' states that sustainable development should take a holistic view towards progress, and should give equal importance to non-economic aspects of well-being and happiness. In Bhutan, one wants to stimulate the set-up of initiatives that aim to increase the percentage of happy people and decrease the unsatisfactory conditions of unhappy people. Recently, in 2013, UN Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon pointed again to the importance of attention for people's well-being and happiness. In his Note to the General Assembly (2013, p. 3) he indicated that '*the creation of an enabling environment for improving people's well-being is a development goal in itself*'. This paper aims to propose a first answer to his call, as it aims to reflect on the concrete contribution that architecture and interior architecture can have in designing 'enabling

environments' wherein people can engage in meaningful activities that contribute to their happiness.

The first section of the paper elaborates about happiness and its determinants, and the potential that architecture and interior architecture can have in this respect. In the second section, a selection of techniques for exploring happiness and for gaining insight in factors contributing to happiness are discussed. Here, the results of a first exploratory study are reviewed. We examine the development and results of the use of a 'Happiness Circle', an instrument which was used to gain insight in the (specific) contribution that architecture and interior architecture have regarding happiness.

Happiness and design

As discussed in the introduction, the changing societal and material conditions seem to be an important breeding ground to the growing attention for research on happiness, also in design sciences. To date, researchers from diverse disciplines ranging from philosophy, psychology, economics and neurosciences have tried to point to the essence of well-being and happiness. In addition, the last few years, different researchers from various design disciplines begun to investigate whether their discipline can contribute to the happiness of people – and if so, what this contribution can look like or how it can be set up or produced. However, to date, there is no consensus on the conceptualization of well-being and happiness (Lyubomirsky, 2007 ; Sheldon & Lyubomirsky, 2007), not in disciplines other than design who focus on well-being and happiness (Lee et al., 2011 ; Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013), nor in design disciplines itself that focus on this topic (Authors, 2014). As a consequence, researchers in academia often use the terms of '(subjective) well-being' and 'happiness' interchangeably (Lyubomirsky, 2007). In this paper, we follow suit.

Etymologically, "well-being" is derived from the Latin verb "velle", meaning to wish, will or literally, "to be" "well". As was mentioned earlier, no universal or specific definition can be given (Lee et al., 2011). However, most researchers agree that the concept has distinctive components: an affective part that has its evaluation based on emotions and feelings, a cognitive part that relies on memories, stored information and barometers based on expectations upon life quality and a contextual part, that relates to the context proper to all individuals (Galinha & Pais-Ribeiro, 2011; Desmet and Pohlmeier, 2013).

Determining happiness: genetics, life circumstances and intentional activities

Although there is no common shared terminology relating to happiness, various researchers share the viewpoint that happiness has an objective and a subjective component (Veenhoven et al., 2014 ; Authors, 2014). In addition, different researchers seem to agree that happiness is determined for a large part by a predefined genetic happiness set-point, which contributes to happiness for 50%, life circumstances (10%) and intentional activities (40%)

Figure 1. What determines happiness?
Source: Lyubomirsky et al., 2005

(Lyubomirsky et al., 2005a ; Lyubomirsky, 2007) (see Figure 1).

Regarding the genetic set-point of happiness, studies have demonstrated that this factor is stable over time and mostly immune to influence (Lykken & Tellegen, 1996; Tellegen et al., 1988).

Therefore, in what follows, the authors elaborate about 'life circumstances' and 'intentional activities', and indicate how, in their view, the subjective and objective approach towards happiness can be integrated herein.

Life circumstances

This factor relates to happiness-relevant circumstantial factors that occur in the course of a person's life and that influence happiness. Life circumstances refer to the national, geographical and cultural region where a person is living, as well as demographic variables such as gender or age. Also issues such as occupational status, income, job security, health status at a particular moment in life, religious affiliation and marital status form part of this happiness-determining factor (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005a).

Research by Diener et al. (1999) has indicated that these variables contribute to happiness, but only to a relatively small extent, as was demonstrated in Figure 1. This seems surprising and even stands out against most people's intuition, but research has learned that the relative small effect of life circumstantial factors can be attributed for a large part to hedonic adaptation (that is, people experience a temporary boost in happiness due to circumstantial factors, but this boost often does not last long because people tend to adapt to changing circumstances rather rapidly) (Lucas, 2007).

Life circumstances concern factors that cannot (easily) be changed. Many of these circumstantial factors relate to issues that help to answer the question *what people have to face* in their lives. Many of these factors can be objectively articulated in a particular way: people *have* a religion affiliation at a particular

time in their lives or they don't, people *have* a particular occupational and marital status at a particular time in their lives, etc. As research has demonstrated, these life circumstances influence happiness, and thus can be considered as 'mediators' for human happiness.

However in the authors' view, life circumstances or 'mediators' cannot easily or solely make people happy. In addition, there are also factors contributing to happiness for which it is not evident to pinpoint exactly whether they concern a 'mediator' or an 'activity' that potentially contributes to happiness; in our view, it depends on the particular lens applied when studying these factors and the potential added value that they can have regarding happiness. In the following sections and also in Table 1 later in this paper, this issue will be discussed in more detail.

Intentional activities

As is clear from Figure 1, there is one factor left which relates to a promising way to work on happiness: intentional activities. These activities relate to behavior, a factor that is within people's ability to control. By focusing on activities, people have the ability to *deliberately* increase their happiness through what they *do* in their lives and how they *think* (Lyubomirsky, 2007). Research on happiness-increasing activities has demonstrated that such activities work, both in the short and the long term (Sin & Lyubomirsky, 2009; Lyubomirsky & Layous, 2013).

There are some important issues to remark in this respect. Firstly, the notion of 'intentional' is important, as people have to deliberately make the choice and be motivated to engage in activities that are meaningful for them (Lyubomirsky et al., 2011). Secondly, a good person-activity fit is indispensable in this respect: taken into account that people have different interests, talents, values, needs and wants, some activities might work for some people but not for others. Thirdly, it is assumed that intentional activities require some degree of effort from the people undertaking and maintaining them: people really have *to do something*, and be actively involved.

This point is a critical distinction between life circumstances and intentional activities. As Lyubomirsky et al. (2005a) state: '*... circumstances happen to people, and activities are ways that people act on their circumstances*'. For instance, it can be that a person has a particular work affiliation at a particular moment in his life (the fact of having a work affiliation is a life circumstance) but that at another moment in his life, this person deliberately undertakes action to change this (actively looking for other work and going to job interviews thus concerns an 'intentional activity'). In addition to people's motivation, efforts and beliefs in engaging in meaningful activities, their personality also is an important factor in determining what people potentially have to gain from engaging in a particular activity (Lyubomirsky & Layous, 2013). Ideally, an intentional activity results in boosting positive emotions, positive behavior, positive thoughts and

satisfaction of needs of the person engaging in the activity (Nelson et al., 2015).

In the view of different researchers from positive psychology (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005a; Lyubomirsky, 2007; Lyubomirsky & Layous, 2013), intentional activities appear to be the best possible way for people to work on their happiness. In the authors' view, focusing on activities opens tremendous possibilities for design to contribute to the happiness of people. Looking specifically at the potential contribution that architecture and interior architecture can have in this respect, it seems highly valuable to consider these as 'spaces' where people can deliberately set up intentional activities that contribute to their happiness (Authors, 2014). There is a huge challenge in further exploring how architects and interior architects can design spaces in such a way so that they can function as a generous, inspiring and fruitful context wherein people can set up meaningful activities that contribute to their happiness.

Happiness, architecture and interior architecture: refining the determinants of happiness

In terms of semantics, subjective well-being (SWB) has different connotations: 'to be well', and 'to feel well'. In the authors' viewpoint, the first conceptualization ('to be well') relates to happiness-relevant circumstantial factors, which have been discussed in the previous section. Looking at life circumstances from an architectural perspective, typical questions in this respect are: 'Am I physically healthy?', 'Do I have a shelter?' etcetera.

The second conceptualization of SWB ('to feel well') relates to more subjective parameters with regards to well-being, and bring us to the importance of intentional activities. Looking at this factor from an architectural perspective leads us to questions such as: 'Can I be happy in this environment?', 'Does the environment enable me to work on my personal happiness?' etcetera. In this description, personal viewpoints and subjective issues are at stake, which can be considered as potential '*consequences*' of the environment wherein one resides. In the authors' viewpoint, it is this second conceptualization that seems particularly interesting and inspiring from the perspective of architects and interior architects who want to focus and work on the happiness of people. Being happy in an environment has to do with what people who reside in a particular architectural or interior environment are able to do with and in that environment, or, put differently, how the environment enables them to do something meaningful or something that adds meaning and pleasure to their life.

Reflecting about these different conceptualizations of SWB from an architectural perspective brought us to refining Figure 1, as in the authors' view, there are factors contributing to happiness which sometimes can be labelled as an 'intentional activity' but which at other times can be labelled as a 'life circumstance' (see Figure 2). For instance, it can be that a person has

Figure 2. Refining Lyubomirsky's determinants of happiness circumstance or activity?

Figure 3. Refining Lyubomirsky's determinants of happiness from the viewpoint of architecture and interior architecture.

a particular religious affiliation at a particular moment in his life (the fact of having a religious affiliation is a life circumstance) but that at another moment in his life, this person deliberately undertakes action to change this (practicing religion thus becomes an issue for which 'intentional activities' are undertaken).

In addition, there are factors contributing to happiness which concern a 'life circumstance' (for instance, architecture and interior architecture, see the grey arrow in Figure 3), but which can function as an enabling *context or platform* where people can set up intentional activities that meaningfully contribute to their happiness.

Architecture and interior architecture: a circumstantial factor that contributes to enabling activities

In the authors' view, a building or interior as such cannot make a person happy. Architecture or interior architecture relate to a circumstantial factor which can only contribute to happiness by designing a *context* wherein *activities* can take place or can be organized which possibly can contribute to a person's happiness. Designing such contexts is challenging, because it requires a designer to truly empathize with the future users of the concerned context. Sometimes this will concern an individual, namely when an architect or interior architect is working for an individual paying client. Here, empathizing with the future user is mostly straightforward, as there is the possibility of truly having a close contact and relationship. But at other times, architects or interior architects will be asked to design a future health care facility, a school, or an office environment. Empathizing in such projects is truly challenging, as architects or interior architects are required to dive into the worldview of the concerned target group, get to know the needs and wants of the different stakeholders involved and have to do a meaningful effort in trying to combine these different sources of input into a valuable architectural or interior architectural concept that can appeal and answer to the different stakeholders' longings and aspirations.

Exploring the impact of architecture and interior architecture on happiness

As mentioned before, there is already a wide array of research in positive psychology about happiness and happiness-enhancing strategies. However, to date, it is recognized that '*researchers do not yet fully understand the causal role of the mediating factors that lead to improved well-being*' (Nelson et al., 2015, p. 256). Nelson & Lyubomirsky (2014) point to the relevance and importance of future research to investigate the '*underlying mechanisms that lead positive activities to successfully improve well-being – that is, the 'why' question ...*' (p. 5). In their view, if research could succeed in identifying why particular activities are effective in enhancing happiness, it will be possible to gain a better insight in the determinants of happiness. In addition, these insights can have important repercussions regarding potential tools that can be designed to help people to work on their happiness. In this section of the paper, the authors discuss an attempt which they undertook to answer Nelson & Lyubomirsky's 2014 call.

Primary and secondary analysis of happiness

In their paper on 'measuring and comparing happiness', Van Praag & Ferrer-i-Carbonell (2010) differentiate between a primary and secondary analysis of happiness.

Primary analysis of happiness: are you happy?

In Van Praag & Ferrer-i-Carbonell's view (2010), a primary analysis entails calculating the individual scores which research participants give to separate items which were added to a happiness measurement instrument in order to come to a general happiness score. The results of such analyses allow to differentiate between the proportion of people who are happy and unhappy, whereby different variables such as age, income, gender etcetera can be taken into account.

As Lyubomirsky (2007) and Veenhoven (2014) recognize, there is currently no widely accepted 'happiness measurement instrument', which is not illogical taken into account the inherent subjective character of happiness. As happiness is always subjective, it is

difficult for others than the concerned person whose happiness one aims to measure, to objectively assess a person's happiness level. As such measure does not yet exist, researchers focusing on happiness today mostly rely on the methodology of self-report. Here, research participants indicate to what extent they perceive themselves to be 'happy'.

In this line of thought, Lyubomirsky & Lepper (1999) developed the 'Subjective Happiness Scale', consisting of a four item measurement which results in a general 'happiness score', but there are numerous other happiness self-report measures possible (for an overview, see Veenhoven, 2012). According to Van Praag & Ferrer-i-Carbonell (2010, p. 7) self-report questions concern *'the prototype of the happiness questions, which form the basic instrument for all studies in happiness economics'*.

Secondary analysis of happiness: why are you happy?

Secondary analysis goes a step further and dives deeper, as it does not try to measure how happy a person is, but aims to find out *why* a person experiences happiness. This kind of analysis tries to find determining factors that can help to explain why individuals are happy or unhappy. This type of analysis is what Nelson & Lyubomirsky (2014) were calling for. In what follows, we discuss the set-up of a secondary analysis instrument which aimed to gain insight in the importance of architecture and interior architecture in the happiness of people.

Gaining insight in factors or determinants of happiness of users of a(n interior) space is the starting-point to understand or try to capture how architecture and interior spaces work, are perceived or can be designed in order to allow people to undertake meaningful activities that contribute to their happiness. If designers could have better insights in the ways in which people perceive and experience environments, and how these potentially contribute to their happiness, they could be enabled to design more 'appealing' atmospheres and environments which in turn could enable people to set up meaningful activities that contribute to their happiness.

An explorative study with a Happiness Circle

In order to further reflect about the potential contribution that architecture or interior architecture might have in contributing to a person's happiness, it is important to gain insight in their role in this respect. Therefore, we designed a 'Happiness Circle'. This instrument can be considered as an explorative tool that aims to gain insight in the different factors that contribute to a person's happiness.

Research objective

Previous research (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005b; Nelson et al., 2015; Lyubomirsky & Layous, 2013; Veenhoven et al., 2014) has demonstrated that there are different sources for enhancing human happiness. In order to further reflect about the potential contribution that architecture or interior architecture might have in contributing to a person's happiness, it is important to gain insight in their role in this respect. Therefore, we designed a 'Happiness Circle' (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. The Happiness Circle.

Development of a Happiness Circle

Research on happiness has pointed to the importance of different factors of happiness:

- health or physical well-being (Achat et al., 2000 ; Lyubomirsky et al., 2005b)
- personal development (Bauer et al., 2015 ; Straume & Vitterso, 2015)
- having work (Graham et al., 2004 ; Lucas et al., 2004)
- having friends / social contacts (Diener & Seligman, 2002 ; Burger & Caldwell, 2000)
- time for oneself / time for hobbies or things that I like (Mishra, 1992 ; Nimrod, 2008)
- family, children, partner (Diener et al., 2000 ; Hansen, 2010)
- music (Laukka, 2007 ; Fujiwara et al., 2014)
- religion (Berg, 2010 ; Myers, 2013)
- holiday, excursions (Gilbert & Abdullah, 2004 ; Nawijn & Veenhoven, 2011)
- money (Diener & Biswas-Diener, 2002 ; Berg, 2010)
- nature, garden, wood, mountains, sea (Van Herzele & de Vries, 2012 ; MacKerron & Mourato, 2013)
- weather (Fischer & Van de Vliert, 2011 ; Connolly, 2013)

These factors were listed after a thorough review of literature, which was performed via an extensive search through the World Database of Happiness (<http://worlddatabaseofhappiness.eur.nl/>). Here, different publications pointed to the relevance of having friends / social contacts, health, time for personal development, having work, family / children / partner, money, music, religion, holiday / excursions, factors relating to nature, weather and having time for oneself. This overview does not pretend to be exhaustive, but aims to list important mediating factors and intentional activities that can contribute to happiness.

Given our interest in a potential contribution of architecture and interior architecture, the factors of 'house (architecture)' and 'interior architecture' were added to our list.

In essence, the factors which were selected are all significant in their contribution to happiness, but they do not contribute to the same extent to happiness;

they concern factors of a different 'order'. Relating each of these factors to the determinants of happiness which were discussed in the first section of the paper (that is, life circumstances, intentional activities and the refining which the authors did in-between these categories of determinants of happiness) results in the following overview (Table 1).

Research procedure

The Happiness Circle (see Figure 4) was part of a short questionnaire which started with four questions relating to socio-demographic variables (i.e., age, gender, education and professional status). Next to these socio-demographic variables, the questionnaire presented a circle to the respondents. They were asked to complete a 'Happiness Circle' which aimed to gain insight in the different factors that contributed to their happiness.

Research participants were free to add other factors than the ones listed in Table 1, for as long as the total sum of their Happiness Circle would result in 100%. For respondents' ease, the circle was already divided in slices of 5%. Participants could select the factors that they wanted, and needed to determine for themselves to what extent these particular factors contributed to their proper happiness.

17 master students in interior architecture and in architecture helped to gather data in 2015. Each student was instructed to look for at least 12 participants, equally spread over gender and different pre-defined age categories (i.e., 18-37 year, 38-57 year, 58-77 year). None of the participants could have a background in architecture or interior architecture or be professionally employed in this area, to avoid potential bias for the factors 'house (architecture)' or 'interior'.

In the end, the sample consisted of 212 research participants.

Research analyses and research results

The calculation of mean scores demonstrated that 'family / children / partner' was the factor that was most important to our sample (23%), followed by 'health / physical well-being' (21%) and friends / social contacts (11%). This seems logical, taken into account the results of the literature review that was performed to gain insights in the importance of different factors of happiness (see Table 1).

In addition, which is important from our point-of-view, architecture and interior architecture came to the fore as determining factors in the happiness of people (see Table 2). As Table 2 illustrates, they seem to contribute to the same extent to our sample's happiness as religion or nature.

Conclusion

Due to the spirits of our times, different researchers in architecture and interior architecture are starting to reflect about the question how the built environment can contribute to happiness (Smith et al., 2012; Authors, 2014).

But, in order to determine whether it is worthwhile for the discipline to engage in a deliberate focus on design for happiness, it is important to find out if, and if so, to what extent, architecture and interior architecture contribute to happiness. A review of literature on happiness pointed to the relevance of different factors which ranged from circumstantial factors that people just have to face, circumstantial factors that can function as a platform for enabling people to undertake activities, factors which can be a life circumstance or can relate to an activity, or activities

Table 1. Selection of determinants of happiness.

Life circumstance ('mediator')	Circumstantial factors which can trigger an activity	Factors which can be a mediator or which can relate to an activity	Activity	Happiness
				Health of Physical well-being
				Friends, social contacts
				Family, children, partner
		Having work		
			Personal development	
			Time for oneself / time for hobbies or things that one likes	
			music	
		Religion / religious affiliation		
			Holiday, excursions	
Money				
Nature, garden, wood, mountains, sea				
Weather				
	House (architecture)			
	Interior			

contributing to happiness. In this respect, the authors do not pretend that the list of factors determining happiness which they studied is exhaustive. What is renewing in this paper, is that the research and analyses demonstrate that architecture and interior architecture truly contribute to happiness.

In the authors' view, there are numerous opportunities for future research. Firstly, there is a wide array of possibilities of 'contexts' where architecture and interior architecture can have a valuable contribution to happiness. Secondly, future research needs to pinpoint how architects and interior architects can concretely contribute to the design of environments that enable people to undertake activities that contribute to their happiness. This will not always be evident: architects and interior architects in practice do not always work for individual paying clients; they also deliver design for schools, care facilities, office environments, where multiple individuals need to 'live' and 'function' together, and need to be enabled to work on their happiness. In our view, striving for the designing of generous environments which offer various possibilities for current and future users can be a valuable road in this respect. Thirdly, future research also needs to collect more empirical data to make it possible to test concrete research hypotheses that can be relevant for architects and interior architects.

Ultimately, we share the viewpoint of Mary-Ann Knudstrup, a Danish professor in architecture, who recently (2011) stated that 'well-being elements should carry at least as much weight as technical, rational and economic considerations in the process'.

Table 2. Mean scores of determining factors for people's happiness¹.

Variable	N	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Max
Family	212	23,4	13,1	0	85
Health	212	20,9	12,5	0	65
SocialContact	212	10,8	8,9	0	45
TimeforMeExtra	212	8,7	8,1	0	55
TimeforMe	212	8,0	7,2	0	30
Money	212	6,6	6,4	0	30
WorkExtra	212	6,5	8,4	0	50
Work	212	6,5	8,4	0	50
Holiday	212	6,2	7,1	0	35
NatureExtra	212	3,2	5,1	0	25
Nature	212	3,1	5,1	0	25
Home	212	3,0	4,5	0	20
Religion	212	2,3	5,9	0	30
Interior	212	2,2	4,1	0	30
Music	212	1,9	4,3	0	30
PersDevelopm	212	1,9	4,6	0	30
Weather	212	1,3	3,2	0	20
Other1	212	0,9	3,8	0	40

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1 Table 2 differentiates between a factor 'TimeforMeExtra' and 'TimeforMe'. 'TimeforMe' relates to respondents who used the factor 'time for for oneself / time for hobbies or things that one likes' which was proposed next to other determinants of happiness. 'TimeforMeExtra' concerns the items which respondents added to the proposed factors but which in essence concerned factors relating to 'TimeforMe' (e.g., working in the garden, working on my car, having a long sleep, giving attention to my pets). 'WorkExtra' relates to items which respondents added to the proposed factors but which in essence concerned factors relating to 'Work' (e.g., school). 'NatureExtra' concerns the items which respondents added to the proposed factors but which in essence concerned factors relating 'Nature' (e.g., enjoying the seaside).

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Towards an HCI model for eudaimonic growth - A phenomenological inquiry into travelers' serious leisure pursuits and cultivation of character strengths

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Abstract Many people strive for a life characterized by self-growth and meaning, considered to be innate needs, by actualizing their authentic potentials during their lifespans. Positive psychology (PP) has termed this self-development process as eudaimonia—to live a virtuous life. From this perspective, such a life can be attained by individuals through cultivating key character strengths. On the other hand, the fields of leisure and tourism regard eudaimonia as the sustained pursuit of leisure activities that involve specific skills, knowledge, and experience. This study combines these two bodies of knowledge to propose a human-computer interaction (HCI) model that can facilitate individual eudaimonic growth through the serious pursuit of leisure activities applicable to the eTourism platform. By integrating concepts reported in the current literature with the results of our phenomenological investigation, we highlight three key findings to support the development of this model: 1. Individual eudaimonic development can be appreciated from both cross-sectional and developmental perspectives; 2. In addition to performance seeking behavior, individual satisfaction and fulfillment can emerge from the process of exercising one's character strengths; 3. Goal formation and introspection are specific aspects that contribute to the meaning of an experience. The proposed HCI model comprises two interrelated components: a strength-based recommender system and personal reflective journaling informatics. The HCI model assumes that eudaimonic growth can occur when both systems are in action.

Keywords *Serious leisure, Eudaimonia, Positive psychology, eTourism, Positive design*

Background

In search of well-being and authenticity

Recent years have seen increased interest in the investigation of well-being as a fundamental prerequisite for individuals, communities, and society to thrive. Currently, the field of positive psychology (PP; Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000) recognizes two aspects of well-being: hedonia and eudaimonia (Ryan & Deci, 2001). Hedonia refers to the attainment of well-being through the pursuit of pleasure, enjoyment, and instant gratification. It can be measured by the presence of a positive affect, the absence of a negative affect, and satisfaction with one's life. Eudaimonia refers to living a virtuous life, as described by the Aristotelian ideals in Nichomachean Ethics (Aristotle, 2009). Eudaimonia is considered to be a process of self-actualization through the sustained pursuit of a meaningful life and the actualization of the individual's true potential and virtues throughout the lifespan (Ryan & Deci, 2001). Although the activities that pertain to hedonia and

eudaimonia are somewhat similar, differences can be observed: some activities can give rise to both eudaimonia and hedonia, and others give rise only to hedonia (Ryan & Deci, 2001). Eudaimonia is believed to be multi-dimensional and motivated by something deeper than sheer enjoyment; it refers to authentic self-realization and self-growth (Huta & Ryan, 2010; Waterman, Schwartz, & Conti, 2008, p. 73); the fulfillment of one's innate need for autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Ryan & Deci, 2000); psychological well-being (Ryff, 1989); a happy and engaging life filled with empathy and purpose (Seligman, 2002); and the cultivation of individual character strengths for the development of individual potential (Peterson & Seligman, 2004). Last but not least, eudaimonia has also been regarded as a perpetual pursuit rather than a momentary experience. Research on the self-concordance theory (Sheldon & Kasser, 1995, 1998) has suggested that pursuing activities that are congruent with one's personal interests and which fulfill one's innate need for autonomy, competence, and relatedness can lead

the way to a life that is characterized by eudaimonia.

Authentic self and life fulfillment in tourism and leisure studies

Similarly, the quest for an authentic self and life fulfillment are strongly debatable concepts in tourism studies (e.g., E. Cohen, 2012). Initiated by MacCannell's concept of staged authenticity (1976), the notion of authenticity in tourism had been critically scrutinized from various worldviews, including objectivism, constructivism, and existentialism. While the objectivist asserts that authenticity is an inherent quality of toured objects, the constructivist argues that authenticity emerges as a result of a socially constructed interpretation of the genuineness of the toured objects. The discourse on existential authenticity is based on Heidegger's phenomenology of the concept of Dasein (Steiner & Reisinger, 2006), or the unique human capability to question and take responsibility for ones' own existential condition in the world. From this perspective, life has no predefined pattern nor destiny, and one can choose to live an authentic life in an awareness of infinite possibilities, or to live an inauthentic subdued life under the shadow of others. As tourism allows individuals to put aside their routine duties and obligations while away from home, it provides unique opportunities for individuals to reflect on their own identities (N. Wang, 1999), to live in accordance with their authentic selves (Brown, 2013), and to experience self-transformation (Reisinger, 2013a) through travel activities. Nonetheless, well-being research in tourism studies has mainly focused on hedonia (Filep, 2012; Nawijn & Veenhoven, 2012) and physical wellness (Chen & Petrick, 2013). Discourses on existential authenticity encourage the examination of travelers' activities and experiences from a eudaimonic well-being perspective (e.g., Filep, 2009; Kler & Tribe, 2012; Reisinger, 2013b; Voigt, Howat, & Brown, 2010).

Similar to tourism, leisure is considered to be an "uncoerced, contextually framed activity engaged in during free time, which people want to do and, using their abilities and resources, actually do in either a satisfying or fulfilling way (or both)" (Stebbins, 2011, p. 4). The serious leisure perspective (SLP; Stebbins, 2007) identifies three forms of leisure: casual leisure (CL), which is regarded as an intrinsically rewarding activity requiring little or no special training to enjoy; project-based leisure (PBL), which is infrequent or a

one-off moderately complicated leisure activity carried out in free time; and serious leisure (SL), which is defined as the "systematic pursuit of an amateur, hobbyist, or volunteer activity sufficiently substantial, interesting, and fulfilling for participant to find a (leisure) career there in acquiring and expressing a combination of its special skills, knowledge, and experience" (Stebbins & Elkington, 2014, p. 4). Stebbins (1982) identified six significant characteristics (Table 1) that pertain to SL. Additionally, the autotelic nature of leisure activity is compatible with the self-concordance theory (Sheldon & Kasser, 1995, 1998), as previously mentioned. While CL could stem from a hedonic motivation, the pursuit of PBL and SL are likely to be eudaimonically motivated via the gain in positive emotion and meaning; increased sense of mastery, accomplishment, and personal growth; the development of altruism; and strengthened active engagement and positive relationships (S. A. Cohen, 2013; Stebbins, 1997, 2015).

With their common goal of eudaimonia, this study connects two bodies of knowledge: the strength-based PP values in action (VIA) approach (Peterson & Seligman, 2004) and the commitment-centric approach of SLP (Stebbins & Elkington, 2014). VIA consists of six universally prominent virtues and 24 related behavior-based character strengths (Table 2) that are considered to be pathways to human flourishing. By using VIA, we can effectively deconstruct and identify the meaning and function of the individual character strengths associated with serious leisure pursuits.

Design and technology supporting the development of human potential

Technology is now omnipresent and thoroughly integrated into our lives: it enables us to work, play, and express ourselves in such a way that we no longer "use" technology but rather it has become a part of our everyday existence. In other words, technology now has the capacity to redefine and transform us (Sellen, Rogers, Harper, & Rodden, 2009). Traveler experience is no exception, as travelers often interact with different information and communication technologies (ICTs) throughout various stages of their journeys (Benckendorff, Sheldon, & Fesenmaier, 2014). The criteria for evaluating ICT solutions, such as websites and mobile apps, are primarily based on their performance and usability metrics: information quality, ease of use, responsiveness, effectiveness,

Table 1. Textile triads 1, 2, and 3.

Serious leisure – six common characteristics	
Quality	Descriptor
Perseverance	The occasional need to persevere amidst adversity
Leisure career	Career-like pursuits shaped by one's own histories of turning points, stage of achievement, and background contingencies
Significant effort	Exertion of significant personal effort to obtain and develop special knowledge, skill, or ability
Durable outcome	Enrichment, self-actualizing, self-gratification, group accomplishment etc.
Unique ethos	Existence of distinguishing, ideals, values, or guiding beliefs that are shared by members of the serious leisure social world
Identification with pursuit	Strong identification of the participant with the chosen pursuit

efficiency, and the like (Buhalis, Leung, & Law, 2011; Y. A. Park & Gretzel, 2007). Furthermore, most studies have been mainly driven by the use of technology by businesses and management, including consumer demand, technological innovation, and industry functions (Buhalis & Law, 2008). Recent research (McCabe, Sharples, & Foster, 2012) has suggested that the ubiquitousness of technology can be used to create meaningful traveler experiences and individual empowerment. In addition, research in user experience design (Harrison, Tatar, & Sengers, 2007; Hassenzahl, 2013) has led authors to argue that broader attention by paid to the human experience from a phenomenological standpoint. Interaction with technology is regarded “as a form of meaning making in which the artifact and its context are mutually defining and subject to multiple interpretation” (Harrison et al., 2007, p. 6). Thus, designs for technology-enabled travelers’ experience must take into account the dynamic use context, the social situation, and users’ emotions and interests, as well as the underlying motives behind their activities. More than a technology push, in this study, we argue that experience design has the potential to accommodate the latent aspects of that which constitutes a meaningful traveler experience (Calvo & Peters, 2014; see also Riva, Baños, Botella, Wiederhold, & Gaggioli, 2012; J. Wang, Chen, Chen, & Chen, 2011) and to foster the eudaimonic well-being of travelers.

Founded within PP, the field of human-computer interaction (HCI) and design also relates to using ICTs and design solutions to promote humanistic values that foster individual growth and social good. The concept of positive computing (PC) identifies nine determinant factors of well-being, which can be used in the context of the digital experience—positive emotions, motivation and engagement, self-awareness,

mindfulness, resilience, gratitude, empathy, compassion, and altruism (Calvo & Peters, 2014, pp. 85–86). On the other hand, the concept of positive design (PD; Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013) proposes a design framework with three components to promote individual well-being: pleasure, personal significance, and virtue. By consciously and strategically integrating these components in design solutions, we can ultimately stimulate and enable human flourishing.

Towards an HCI model for fostering individual eudaimonic development through cultivation of character strengths and serious leisure pursuits in the context of tourism

The goal of this study is to devise a preliminary HCI model that facilitates individual eudaimonic growth in the serious pursuit of leisure activities applicable to the eTourism platform. We explore the potential use of ICTs that can foster human flourishing through eudaimonic growth. First, we examine the role of participant character strengths that are associated with the construction of meaningful experience in serious leisure activities. Then, we identify common patterns pertaining to eudaimonic development that have emerged from various participants’ serious leisure pursuits. By integrating concepts from the current literature with data collected from this study, we provide some directions for establishing the model. This pilot study addresses the following questions:

- Q1. How to assess individual eudaimonic development from participants’ character strengths and serious pursuit of leisure activity?
- Q2. How to use ICT to better support the cultivation of individual character strengths in serious leisure

Table 2. Values in Action (VIA) Classification of Character Strengths and Virtues (Peterson & Seligman, 2004).

Values in Action (VIA) Classification of Character Strengths and Virtues			
Virtues	Character strengths	Virtues	Character strengths
Wisdom	Creativity – originality, adaptive, ingenuity;	Transcendence	Appreciation of beauty & excellence – awe, wonder, elevation;
	Curiosity – interest, novelty-seeking, exploration, openness to experience;		Gratitude – thankful for the good, expressing thanks, feeling blessed,
	Judgment – critical thinking, thinking things through, open-minded;		Hope – optimism, future-mindedness, future orientation;
	Love of learning – mastering new skills & topics, systematically adding to knowledge;		Humor – playfulness, bringing smiles to others, lighthearted;
	Perspective – wisdom, providing wise counsel, taking the big picture view.		Spirituality – religiousness, faith, purpose, meaning
Courage	Bravery – valor, not shrinking from fear, speaking up for what’s right;	Temperance	Forgiveness – mercy, accepting others’ shortcomings, giving people a second chance;
	Perseverance – persistence, industry, finishing what one starts;		Humility – modesty, letting one’s accomplishments speak for themselves;
	Honesty – authenticity, integrity;		Prudence – careful, cautious, not taking undue risks;
	Zest – vitality, enthusiasm, vigor, energy, feeling alive and activated.		Self-regulation – self-control, disciplined, managing impulses & emotions;
Humanity	Love – both loving and being loved, valuing close relations with others;	Justice	Teamwork – citizenship, social responsibility, loyalty;
	Kindness – generosity, nurturance, care, compassion, altruism, “niceness”;		Fairness – just, not letting feelings bias decisions about others;
	Social intelligence – emotional intelligence, aware of the motive/feelings of self/others, knowing what makes other people tick.		Leadership – organizing group activities, encouraging a group to get things done.

pursuits?

Q3. How the use of ICT can facilitate individual levels of commitment and performance in serious leisure pursuits?

Research methodologies

This study references both the constructivism viewpoint of phenomenology and the post-positivism viewpoint of the normative virtue ethics advocated by Aristotle's *Nicomachean Ethics*. We acknowledge that individual sense making and experience of serious leisure are highly contextual and are influenced by the complex and ever-changing social phenomena encountered (Gillespie & Cornish, 2010). As argued by Peterson & Seligman (2004), different people can flourish differently in their own configuration despite identical achievements. We use two models in this study: serious leisure pursuit (SLP) and strengths-based values in action development (VIA). SLP recognizes the developmental aspect of leisure pursuits and considers the transition between casual leisure, project-based leisure, and serious leisure activities as a continuum rather than as dichotomies (Shen & Yarnal, 2010). They can be described as a progression from dabbler to core devotee through six SLP characteristics (Table 1). The VIA strength-based model identifies a mix of character traits that can resonate with an individual's inner self (demon) (N. Park, Peterson, & Seligman, 2004).

Research plan and instruments

For this research, we used a questionnaire and in-depth one-on-one interviews to probe the character strengths that participants had drawn upon in their serious leisure activities during their journeys. Overall, we used two qualitative inquiry approaches: thematic analysis (Boyatzis, 1998) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (Smith & Osborn, 2007). We used the questionnaire, based on VIA, to identify themes to guide subsequent in-depth interviews. By carrying out both deductive and inductive thematic investigations, we were able to obtain valuable information during the study.

Online questionnaire

The purpose of the self-administered questionnaire was to help us to identify the signature character strengths that participants had drawn upon in their serious leisure pursuits—not to conduct quantitative and statistical analyses. From the responses to this questionnaire, we shortlisted three to seven character strengths most relevant to the participants' leisure pursuits (Niemi, 2013). We then used these strengths to guide our thematic interviews and in the coding scheme for data analysis. The online questionnaire comprised 142 questions with 3 main parts: 1. Background and experience of the participants in serious leisure; 2. Self-reported appraisal of each participant's character strengths upon which they had drawn in their leisure pursuits; 3. Their use of ICTs at various stages of their leisure pursuits. Regarding the self-reported appraisal, each character strength was addressed in five questions or statements relating to: 1. The relevance of the character strength in contributing to their life fulfillment; 2. Self-

appreciation of the importance of the contribution of the character strength to eudaimonia; 3. The extent to which their character strength can be developed through their serious leisure pursuits; 4. The extent to which the participant must use each character strength to excel in their leisure pursuits; and 5. The extent to which practicing the serious leisure pursuit during their journey can foster the participants' character strengths. For example, the five questions related to the character strength "curiosity" are as follows:

1. To be curious is an important personal character trait that can bring me a life of meaning and fulfillment;
2. I have strong sense of curiosity;
3. The serious leisure pursuit (to be replaced with the name of the serious leisure activity in which the participant is involved) allows me to be more curious;
4. To excel in the serious leisure pursuit (to be replaced with the name of the serious leisure activity in which the participant is involved) requires me to be more curious;
5. Practicing serious leisure pursuit (to be replaced with the name of the serious leisure activity in which the participant is involved) during my journey made me more curious.

We used a five-level Likert Scale, ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. We then added up the five scores pertaining to each character strength and considered those character strengths that ranked higher (the topmost 3-7 character strengths, according to VIA recommendation; Niemi, 2013) to be the participants' signature character strengths that were contributing to their serious leisure pursuits. These highlighted character strengths were emphasized and further discussed in the in-depth interviews with each participant.

Semi-structured in-depth interview guide

Based on the results of the questionnaire, we then focused on a manageable number of character strengths to be discussed in the interview. We adopted the interpretative phenomenological analysis approach in which the researcher facilitates participants' sharing of their life stories and anecdotes (Pietkiewicz & Smith, 2014). Participants were encouraged to use object and photo elicitations as means to enrich the discussions.

Sampling

In this pilot study, we expected the sample to represent the depth and breadth of the serious leisure landscape. We used heterogeneous, non-probability, and purposive samples. We consider that serious leisure can be practiced regardless of age, educational background, household composition, or profession. Furthermore, character strengths are seen to be cross-cultural (McGrath, 2015; Seligman, Steen, Park, & Peterson, 2005), which frees the sampling procedure from demographic concerns. However, the participants deemed to be suitable for this study had to fulfill two criteria: they were to be serious leisure practitioners in any of the domains identified by Stebbins (1982);

and they must have practiced their SL, either partially or entirely, in one or more of their journeys. Below, we identify six broad SL domains and offer a few examples:

1. Art and culture: language and culture, culinary arts, painting, photography;
2. Sports: scuba diving, yachting, mountaineering, running marathons, rock climbing;
3. Natural sciences: amateur cosmologist, amateur radio enthusiast, organic farming;
4. Entertainment: magic, drama, singing, performance dance;
5. Volunteering: education, first aid, humanistic work, environmental protection;
6. Spirituality: yoga, meditation, pilgrimage, spiritual practice.

We recruited participants using convenient and snowball sampling methods through various social networks to connect with different SL communities. We introduced ourselves through email or telephone to potential participants to communicate the project objectives. We invited a total of seven people to participate in this study, each of whom participated in a different SL genre with various degrees of commitment. All participants were of Chinese ethnicity, and lived and worked in Hong Kong at the time of the interview. Table 3 lists the participants' backgrounds, SL activities, experience, and a personal statement on their SL pursuits.

Data collection, coding scheme

We conducted interviews in the native (Cantonese) language of the participants so that they could freely express their views without any language constraints. The interviews began with a self-introduction by the participants and their experience in SL, followed by thematic discussions based on the list of character strengths highlighted in their responses to the online questionnaire. The duration of each interview was around 90 minutes and the interview sessions were audio recorded, translated, and then transcribed into

English edited text for further data analysis. A research assistant helped in the transcription and coding process, during which the coding scheme and coding procedure was discussed. We used the VIA (Table 2) and SL characteristics (Table 1) as references in the coding scheme. We performed the coding using QSR NVivo software, and applied the codes to the sentences and paragraphs of the transcript.

Visual representation of data analysis

In addition to coding, visualization is another means for understanding the dynamics of the participants' character strengths that interplay with their SL activities and their attributed meaning. We used a thematic map (Braun & Clarke, 2006) and the actor network theory (ANT; Latour, 1999) to examine the connections between human and non-human entities. From the ANT perspective, the "actor" can be literally anything as long as it is regarded as the source of action and has the capability to influence other "actor(s)". A "network" is generated by connecting different actors. Meaning emerges as a result of the interplay between networked actors with respect to subject, objects, social networks, environment, situations, interactions, and emotions. The ANT map illustrates the complexity of eudaimonic development. We also use a swim lane diagram to illustrate how SL activities are associated with participants' development of SL pursuits over time.

Results

Background of the participants

Here, we provide a brief introduction to the participants' backgrounds to better convey their ideas of eudaimonia with respect to their serious leisure pursuits. To preserve privacy, all identifying information has been changed.

Emily, a new environmental science graduate, loves to be in contact with nature. Hiking, planting, and identifying insect species are her preferred activities that connect her with her passion and reflect the

Table 3. List of participants, background, and personal statement on their serious leisure pursuits.

List of participant, background, and personal statement on their serious leisure pursuits				
Pseudonym ¹	Domain	Activity	Experience (year)	Statement ²
Emily	Natural science	WWOOF3	1	To experience beauty and harmony in organic farming with friends.
Kelly	Entertainment	Swing dance	7	Swing dancing gives me a vibrant life.
Sofia	Art & Culture	Documentary photography	10	Capturing the authenticity of other cultures helps me to reflect on my identity.
Shane	Sport	Rock climbing	8	Be humble, there are always higher "mountains" ahead.
Evan	Sport	Dinghy racing	13	Dinghy racing connects me to the flow of life.
Orion	Spirituality	Theravada meditation	7	Meditation makes a better version of me.
Andy	Volunteer	Volunteer on education project	7	We work for equal learning opportunity, and it is through learning that more opportunities can be provided to everyone.

¹ Name and details of the participants are changed to preserve confidentiality.

² Statements were formulated based on the data collected in the interview.

³ WWOOF refers to World Wide Opportunities on Organic Farms, a networks of organizations that facilitate overseas' work placements on organic farming.

beauty and harmony of nature. Recently, she launched herself as a WWOOFer (World Wide Opportunities on Organic Farms) and has toured overseas with friends to further explore the wonders of nature. Considering it as a once-in-a-lifetime experience, she was curious about what WWOOFing would offer. Strictly defined, her case can be considered as project-based leisure (Stebbins, 2011), which may have the potential to transform into a sustained pursuit.

Sofia's passion for documentary photography is closely connected with tourism. Through the camera lens, she enjoys capturing the authentic everyday lives of people in other cultures. Travelling away from home allows her to reflect on her personal identity while putting her daily routine aside. The curiosity she has about other cultures creates an introspective space in which she finds herself better able to appreciate the cultural diversities of other societies.

Kelly is a performance artist. She became interested in swing dance during an overseas tour. She likes to dance for a number of reasons: the funky jazz music, the freedom of bodily movement and expression, the stylish dress code of the 1950s, and the welcoming community. Soon after learning to dance, she became an active member in the dance community, attending overseas competitions and workshops. She also hopes to introduce dance in her local community through workshops and gatherings.

Shane met her husband in the rock climbing community. Their romance developed, not through mass tourism experiences, but at various rock climbing sites around the globe. Recently, they spent a year touring around Europe with a focus on experiencing different natural rock formations. Climbing has made Shane more humble and self-controlled when facing the challenges of an ever-changing natural environment.

Evan launched herself into dinghy racing endeavors. Her determination and skill has brought her to the point of being a candidate in world championships. Pursuing performance, mastery, and direct contact with the ocean has made her totally devoted to these pursuits. Fulfillment has come through her bravery and perseverance. This immersive sporting experience captivated her despite the routine and tough physical training in adverse conditions.

While SL is obviously associated with sport endeavors, Orion decided to pursue another extreme by becoming a serious practitioner of meditation. Instead of pursuing hedonic enjoyment, she was determined to find more sustained fulfillment through this practice. She has found honesty and self-acceptance to be the essence of wisdom. Prolonged meditation retreats, which can last from 10 days to months, has led to experiences of both epiphany as well as misery.

Andy was invited by his friends to initiate a charity project when he was an undergraduate student. The group started to build primary schools in rural areas of Cambodia. He became devoted to the project and, in subsequent years, built a few schools in Cambodian

villages with more and more volunteers joining every year. For him, gratitude and learning characterize this project in every sense of the word. While the group builds places for learning, Andy finds that he himself learns a lot from these building projects.

Despite the diverse backgrounds, motives and goals of the participants, their activities qualify as falling within the constellation of serious leisure pursuits, as noted by Stebbins (1982), through various combinations of character strengths. Some commonalities can be identified: 1. The pursuit of serious leisure can be appreciated from both cross-sectional and developmental perspectives; 2. Individual satisfaction and fulfillment can be achieved through exercising one's character strengths, in addition to performing the activity itself; 3. Goal formulation, reflection, and introspection are important aspects of building meaningful experiences.

Cultivation of character strengths in the context of serious leisure pursuits

Through in-depth interviews, we further examined details associated with these SL pursuits. We used the stories and anecdotes recounted by participants as well as the relevant codes as references to support the three key findings noted above.

1. Appreciation of serious leisure from cross-sectional and developmental perspectives

The practice of any form of serious leisure requires more than one character strength. As such, this study does not attempt to make generalizations about how to pair the character strengths of any leisure activity. As described by SLP and VIA, eudaimonia is the result of a sustained commitment and cultivation of character strengths in autotelic activities. The stories shared by the participants reveal eudaimonia to be a dynamic concept that can be viewed from both synchronic (cross-sectional) and diachronic (developmental) perspectives.

As an example, we can use the swing dancing that Kelly performs to illustrate these two perspectives. With reference to the coded transcript matching within the VIA framework, we can identify four dominant character strengths, using the coding reference number of the transcript shown in the brackets: social intelligence (18), kindness (11), zest (9), and love of learning (7). From the synchronic perspective (Figure 1), swing dancing is composed of an array of interlinked activities, whereas dance performance is only one aspect of this pursuit. Social intelligence is the character strength most strongly connected with the activities related to her dance performance.

In addition to the cross-sectional aspects, Kelly's swing dance pursuits can also be appreciated from a developmental perspective (Figure 2). Her 7-year pursuit of swing dance has been marked by numerous memorable and personally significant achievements and milestones: regular gatherings, intensive workshops, meetings with like-minded people, festivals, winning a championship in a dancing contest, and promoting dance to others. These

Figure 1. ANT diagram of Kelly's character strengths related to her swing dance pursuits from a cross-sectional perspective.

achievements can be viewed with respect to the six defined SLP characteristics involving the incremental acquisition of knowledge, skill, and experience, and sustained personal effort (Stebbins, 1982). Appreciating eudaimonic development from the cross-sectional and development perspectives is important with respect to technology because technology, such as personal informatics (Li, 2011), has become an integral part of everyday life. While current informatics systems focus on aggregating bio-signals, we propose an informatics system that focuses on the development of individual character strengths over time.

2. Pursuing serious leisure involves more than performance; satisfaction and fulfillment can be achieved through exercising individual character strengths

According to the SLP concept, pursuing serious leisure is primarily focused on excelling in contextually framed activities through an accumulation of individual skills, knowledge, and experience through persistent effort. However, in this paper, we argue that serious leisure pursuit involves more than just performance (e.g., Scott & Godbey, 1994). For example, one of the important things Shane has learned from her rock climbing pursuit is personal humility--balancing personal performance with the demands of the immediate environment, especially when confronting adverse weather conditions:

"For me, climbing is not about excitement... It is about humility. First, you cannot climb when it is a rainy day. The climbing community is very international and there are always many outstanding climbers around." Wan, B. (Interviewer) & Shane (Interviewee). (2015). In-depth interview - Flourishing through travel [Interview transcript].

Besides performance and self-identity, the quest for an authentic self is also an important aspect of serious leisure pursuit. Orion's motivation for pursuing meditation is the journey to find her genuine self:

"The more you are involved in [meditation] practice, the more you gain insight into yourself... I was intrigued and curious to know more about myself." Wan, B. (Interviewer) & Orion (Interviewee). (2015). In-depth interview - Flourishing through travel [Interview transcript].

The in-depth interviews with participants showed that serious leisure is a complex phenomenon. With reference to the six SLP characteristics (Stebbins, 1982), SL seems able to address the identification and development of self-identity (Goffman, 1959). Using the VIA model, we can identify the intrinsic qualities of the authentic self—the implicit quality of eudaimonia.

3. Goal formulation and introspection are peculiar to serious leisure pursuit

The results of this research suggest that formulating and pursuing self-concordant goals that are compatible with personal signature character strengths can foster one's eudaimonic growth (e.g., Sheldon & Kasser, 1995). One example is that by participating in WWOOFing activities, Emily found that they resonated with her love of learning. Evan found that once she had established numerous goals, they brought her both positive and negative experiences. She has found her 13-year pursuit of dinghy racing to bring her into the flow of life, even though it has not become her career, as she had once expected. Perseverance, zest, and bravery are the character strengths that connect her with her growth-goal.

Quality of Serious Leisure Perspective

Journey map shows Kelly's commitment to Swing Dance in terms of SLP (developmental perspective)

Figure 2. Swim lane diagram illustrating Kelly's commitment to swing dance as an SLP, from a developmental perspective.

Another common aspect of participants in SL pursuits is their capacity for reflection and introspection with respect to their goal attainment. Andy's 7-year experience as a volunteer in school building projects in Cambodia has caused him to seriously reflect on his actions:

"After years of field work, we [the team] always reflect on the rationale behind our activities; what is the purpose of our field work? Is it to show our achievements to others? Or to make ourselves experts in school building? Are we actually doing 'good' for the local people?"

"A recent article I read was about an orphanage visit that turned into a lucrative business opportunity for local tour agencies... we keep learning what's happening out there and constantly reflect on our own practices." Wan, B. (Interviewer) & Andy (Interviewee). (2015). In-depth interview - Flourishing through travel [Interview transcript].

Introspection about the goal attained in connection with the participants' life purpose is also a common theme in SL pursuits. Andy's introspective thoughts about his volunteer work is about more than his self-identity or his initial expectations:

"On many occasions, I have seen sincerity, authenticity, and gratitude through their [people in Cambodia] eyes and actions... that is one of the reasons that keeps me involved in this project. After years of experience, it [the charity work] is no longer a serious leisure pursuit, it has become a mission—an inner calling urged me to return to Cambodia to work on another project." Wan, B. (Interviewer) & Andy (Interviewee). (2015). In-depth interview - Flourishing through travel [Interview transcript].

The results of this study revealed that individual eudaimonic growth through serious leisure pursuits involves individual signature character strengths. By

combining our research findings with concepts in the current literature, we propose a tentative interactive model for promoting and enabling individual character strengths and potentials through serious leisure activities.

Discussion—toward an HCI model for eudaimonic growth

The proposed HCI model (Figure 3) contains two interrelated components: a goal formulation and strength-based recommender system (SBRs; Ricci, Rokach, Shapira, & Kantor, 2011) and a journaling and personal informatics system (JPIS; Li, Dey, & Forlizzi, 2011). These two components coincide with recent findings in eudaimonic development, wherein researchers (Bauer, McAdams, & Pals, 2006; Bauer, Park, Montoya, & Wayment, 2014) have identified two facets of growth motivation: experiential and reflective. The former supports the deepening or strengthening of individual experience and relationships through skill and knowledge building; the latter focuses on the individual's conceptual learning and gaining of new perspectives on one's psychosocial life.

Based on our research results, we hypothesize that eudaimonic growth happens when goal setting and strength building harmonize with reflection and introspection behaviors through journaling. In contrast to personal informatics that focuses on the collection and analysis of bio-signals (Li, Medynskiy, Froehlich, & Larsen, 2012), we propose new considerations that can support eudaimonic well-being in the current technology-enabled culture: First, we suggest the relevance of a strength-based recommender system to facilitate the formulation of growth-goals that specifically address the information overload that occurs over cyberspace. Second, we suggest the use of ICTs for technology-mediated introspection. Reflection and introspection allow individuals to critically reflect on their behavior, by "bringing unconscious aspects of experience to

Design for eudaimonic growth

HCI model that fosters one's eudaimonic growth through cultivation of character strengths in serious leisure pursuits

Figure 3. Tentative HCI model for the fostering of individual eudaimonic growth through the cultivation of character strengths in serious leisure pursuits.

conscious awareness, thereby making them available for conscious choice" (Sengers, Boehner, David, & Kaye, 2005, p. 50). Reflection is not simply an end, but rather it can be integrated into the developmental process to enable eudaimonic growth. Currently, usability and effectiveness remain the main frames of reference for conceptualizing and measuring ICT solutions for tourism and leisure. Here, we call for greater attention to be given to travelers' motives, their core character strengths, and personal reflection as the building blocks of meaningful experience, and which can be integrated into the design of technology-enabled tourist experiences. Further field research through participatory design and prototyping is necessary to explore and validate appropriate design criteria and principles related to the proposed model. Lastly, we acknowledge the limitations of this research. First, the use of more homogenous samples and a larger sample size would better identify existing behavior and strength patterns in SL pursuits. The proposed model suggests the "how" with respect to technology but does not propose the "what" features that can foster eudaimonic growth. Second, a more formalized interview approach and coding procedures should be adopted. Third, the results of this pilot study do not provide sufficient grounds for establishing an HCI model. In-depth studies of the implementation of such a system are needed to verify the merits of this proposal.

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It's alive: An empirical study on animism and animacy in product design

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Abstract The attachment people experience towards products has been the topic of many studies but very little has been written on *animism and product attachment*. Here it is argued that in order to grant a product animated qualities, the user actually requires animistic thinking and it is necessary to translate perceivable characteristics of *animacy* into product language. This is the basis for empirically testing the mutually dependent relationship (of *animism* and *animacy*) using six separate experiments. The hypotheses to be tested assume that a product featuring a defined characteristic is perceived as more alive or more animated than the same product lacking such a characteristic. It is argued here that more product attachment can be achieved not simply through more things “alive” but by actually encouraging a *new animism*.

Keywords *Animism, Animacy, Evolutionary theory, Product design, Product attachment*

Introduction

Our modern consumerism leads to shorter lifespans of products in most categories since older versions of the products are often replaced while still functioning and new products are bought following the slogan „the cheaper, the better“. This is not only the result of planned obsolescence (Packard 1960), but also of obsolescence of desirability. To avoid ecological disaster, some approaches have been suggested: The *Cradle to Cradle* concept (McDonough & Braungart 2010, 2013) as well as *Circular Product Design* (Bakker, 2014) are amongst the most promising. Foremost, this paper is influenced by Jonathan Chapman’s theory of emotionally durable design where the relationships between consumer and product are explored (Chapman 2005, 2009, 2015). Although such considerations are indispensable for a needed design revolution, this paper argues for more attachment to the things we already have. As the things around us become “alive”, is it not feasible to expect more emotionality? The easiest way to encourage the perception of life in products likely is through a product’s appearance and behavior since some crucial criteria for life – such as DNA – cannot be observed. In biological language, we work on the phenotype and not the genotype of an object. In order to focus more on *animacy*, we defined seven characteristics based on Koshland (2002), Bell (2012a, 2012b) and Moskowitz (2012): adaptability, energy, goal-oriented movement, memory, regeneration, sensation and communication. To test which characteristics are required of a product for it to be considered alive we designed a laboratory study and analyzed the findings with regard to design strategies.

Animism and our archaic mind

Any sufficiently advanced technology is indistinguishable from magic. – Arthur C. Clarke (1962)

Talking to inanimate objects is nothing new and humans have likely always done so, but that communication has just transmuted to a dialogue. As our tools’ communication improves, users move in a little closer to listen and respond. We already pinch, tap, touch, hold and talk to our devices and it seems that ironically, Modernity has returned to *animism*, the belief in a soul inside inanimate objects.

The British anthropologist Edward Tylor first articulated the term *animism* calling it the “idea of pervading life and will in nature” (Tylor, 1871). According to Tylor, animism was the most primitive stage in belief systems, followed by a polytheistic and final monotheistic stage. Not an organized religion, to Tylor animism has no institution (e.g. a synagogue, mosque, or church), it does not have an unchangeable doctrine (e.g. a belief in a son of God), and it doesn’t have sacred literature (e.g. the Hebrew Bible or the Quran). From the Latin *anima* (“breath, spirit, life”) it became known as the belief in the possession of a spiritual essence or soul of non-human entities such as animals, plants or inanimate objects. Remarkably, a vast majority of cultures do not have a term for such belief and even the described practitioners of animism do not use the term, suggesting that the phenomenon is little more than a European construct of the 19th century. Undeniably, the term *animism* now stands for traditionalism and for an outdated, even absurd practice. The term also became part of a larger construct of the notion of a time before and after bestowing souls onto things, a time before and after Modernity and nothing more than an anthropological curiosity. Ever since the Enlightenment, modern Europeans have decided to think in terms of subject-object dualism but such a mode of classification was just that: a classification. To a large degree Modernism is actually based on objectifying nature, of doing away with any notion of a subject-subject based relationship. And thus, *animism* – as defined in the

19th century – actually rejects Cartesian dualism and is anchored in the esoteric, non-scientific traditions. Philosopher Bruno Latour laments that we are living in times of wrong epistemologies:

“If there is one thing to wonder about in the history of Modernism, it is not that there are still people “mad enough to believe in animism”, but that so many hard headed thinkers have invented what should be called inanimism and have tied to this sheer impossibility their definition of what it is to be “rational” and “scientific”. It is inanimism that is the queer invention: an agency without agency constantly denied by practice” (Latour, 2010, p. 10).

The danger and far-reaching consequences of such constructed dualities becomes apparent when considering that *unilineal evolutionism* is intrinsically related to *modernization theory* (Rostow, 1990) via the writings of the so-called *neo-evolutionists* (White, 1954). In its final consequence, the idea that all civilizations imperatively have to move through the same stages of development is causally linked to world developmental politics as well as the industrial exploitation of nature. Indeed, the technophile tendencies so rampant in design practices have been diametrically opposed to E.O. Wilson’s “biophilia” (Stairs, 1997).

Recently, anthropologists and comparative-religion scholars have re-defined *animism* to mean something different (Bird-David 1999; Descola 2005, 2006, 2009; Harvey 2005; Ingold 2000). Our relationships with the world and the frontiers between human and nonhuman – even between living and non-living – are being reconsidered. Similarly, the dichotomy of a *before* and *after* in history is senseless. A modern, rational mind never replaced a superstitious, primitive one just like the conquistadores of various eras and nations never found savages on lower evolutionist strata. In short, mistaken epistemologies aren’t replaced. Rather, the human mind perceives and makes sense of the world on different levels of abstraction simultaneously and it is thus important to inject the above epistemological discussions with some biological considerations.

Here we won’t satisfactorily answer the question whether humans are naturally prone to animism, but we can assume that the human species – like all living organism – is a complex product of evolution. We are so good at reasoning on the basis of design from birth onward that it is very likely a genetically evolved adaptation (Wilson, 2011), and thus each one of us truly is a designer. At the dawn of speciation, *Homo habilis* developed the first artifacts, culture was synonymous with design and the designer was Promethean. Ancestral Hominids have failed to evolve many defensive characteristics (Lorenz, 2000), but without a doubt they advanced to become the species most sophisticated at niche construction since we deliberately change most aspects of our environment (Odling-Smee, Laland, & Feldman, 2003). The blueprint for the things we design – hand axes, houses and smartphones – is never genetically anchored but the potential to shape existing matter into new forms and

in new ways likely is. Dennis Dutton believes all forms of design including art are innate, speaks of an *art-instinct* and argues that the production and acquisition of aesthetic objects has brought our ancestors a survival advantage (Dutton, 2009). As will be discussed in more detail below, the designer has to design for the circumstances of the 21st century but he/she should never forget that the end user has an archaic mind.

Product attachment and animacy

A lot of research has been done on designing meaningful and emotionally durable products in order to counteract the modern „throw-away culture“, mainly since the early 1980s and sometimes under different designations (e.g. Schultz, Kleine, & Kernan, 1989; Chapman, 2005, 2009, 2015; Mugge, 2007; Schifferstein & Zwartzkruis-Pelgrim, 2008, Page, 2014). Also, affective sustainability of objects – in other words, the object itself causing sustainable behavior in its user – has been researched (Börjesson, 2009). By considering cognition part of the design process, our everyday things might be longer lasting by adding *animacy* (Norman, 2004). Perhaps the most important researcher in this field, Jonathan Chapman defines waste as a failed relationship between user and object (Chapman, 2015, p. 20). While the first period (“honeymoon”) of possession (e.g. some weeks) between an owner and product is full of excitement, curiosity and interest, these emotions often fade in the course of time. This is often a result of disappointed demands on the products that were raised by advertising messages and decreasing novelty of the products themselves. Therefore the challenge is to keep the product developing and evolving side by side with its owner to preserve an attachment and to reach a longer-lasting honeymoon period full of passion and desire. According to Chapman five points should be considered to prolong an emotional relationship (Chapman, 2009):

- **Narrative:** *users share an evolving history with the product which is often related to the date or place of the acquisition (e.g. souvenirs) or from whom the user got it (e.g. as a present)*
- **Consciousness:** *the product possesses free will or an autonomous mind*
- **Attachment:** *users feel a strong emotional connection to the product which is connected to the service, information or meaning it provides*
- **Fiction:** *the product holds attention because the user cannot fully understand it or know it, especially with a recently bought item*
- **Surface:** *the product ages well and develops character through use (or sometimes misuse), e.g. patina.*

In this paper we focus on the concept *consciousness*, as it is believed that this factor is especially effective in warranting product attachment. We realized that the term *consciousness* is probably too ambitious since something has to be literally alive to be conscious. So we took a step back and stated that *consciousness* actually comes after life is put into something, animating it. The degree of being alive may vary depending on language and their cultural influences. In some languages a tree – for example –

may be seen as alive and in others as inanimate (Malchukov, 2008). Following such considerations, we chose the term *animacy* as “the state of being alive and animated” (Animacy, 2016). “To animate” is a transitive verb, and thus you always need a subject, which actively animates a passive object. Although not a commonly used word, *animacy* should delicately express that the artefact is not actually alive itself but was rather provided with “life” by somebody. “Giving life” is not meant in a procreative, but rather cognitive way. Animate cues are likely those that suggest intrinsic traits such as consciousness, intention, goal-orientation or others normally reserved for living organisms. The famous test by Heider and Simmel (1944) showed that simple geometric shapes (moving triangle, three moving circles and three non-moving squares) are considered animate due to their seeming intentionality. It was even demonstrated that a single, non-anthropomorphized, moving object can create the subjective impression of *animacy* (Tremoulet & Feldman, 2000).

Here, it is assumed that an object considered more alive will be less likely discarded. In order to produce an emotionally charged interface between subject and object, the designer must cater to the *animist* tendencies of the user, who then grants objects *animacy*. As is argued below, these processes are likely unconscious.

Evolution, animacy and the unconscious

It is an oxymoron to *study* the unconscious. For this reason its “discovery” by the founding fathers of psychoanalysis Freud and Jung was not part of the psychological canon until the 1970s when Richard Nisbett and Timothy Wilson demonstrated the difficulty humans have with introspection and/or explication of their own mental processes in a highly cited paper (Nisbett & Wilson, 1977). This phenomenon has actually been labeled “introspection illusion” and is considered a cognitive bias, often leading to a related illusion of superiority. In *Strangers to Ourselves*, Wilson (2004) develops a kind of method of self-knowledge based on action, not feelings or thoughts. Indeed, there are numerous other researchers who argue that intuition is a decision – making process for which reasoning is not consciously available (Bastick 1982, Agor 1986) but all neglect to explain *why* our unconscious might work the way it does. Why might it be adaptive?

Granting objects *animacy* likely happens on an unconscious level. In such a model, the observer must rely on a set of algorithms that grants *animacy* onto some entities but not others. Those algorithms – we believe – were put into place in our species’ evolutionary history due to advantageous outcomes for ancestral individuals. This reasoning belongs to *evolutionary psychology*, which, with its approach to the human psyche using principles of evolutionary theory, is controversial. However, without theoretical underpinning, granting *animacy* would simply be on a long list of illusions, heuristics and cognitive biases. The systematic evolutionary study of the human psyche is young (Barkow, Cosmides, & Tooby, 1992) and argues that Hominids living in small tribes of hunter-

gatherers evolved a psychology for archaic – not modern – circumstances. Science writer Michael Shermer puts it this way:

“What may seem like irrational behavior today may have actually been rational 100,000 years ago. Without an evolutionary perspective, the assumptions of *Homo economicus* – that “Economic Man” is rational, self-maximizing and efficient in making choices – make no sense” (Shermer, 2008).

The aim of evolutionary psychology is to understand the ultimate – not proximate – reasons humans do what they do and it has the following main tenets: (1) Our ancestors faced many dire challenges during our species’ evolutionary history and natural selection designed our ancestors’ neural circuits to solve them. (1) Only those ancestors that were able to solve problems passed their genes on and those genes were used to build more successful neural circuits. (3) Thus, our modern skulls literally house Stone Age minds. (4) Most of the activity in our minds is unconscious and hidden from us. (5) The mind is modular. Different types of neural circuits are all specialized for solving different adaptive problems (Dunbar & Barrett 2007). The question that remains is *why*...was recognizing *animacy* advantageous to our ancestors?

Seeing animals or faces in clouds or the man in the moon, and hearing messages on Black Sabbath records when played in reverse are examples of *paraidolia*, the perception of patterns within random data. *Faces in the Clouds: A new Theory of Religion*, a recent book sees *paraidolia* as part of *animism*, positing that this might be a fitting evolutionary explanation for the birth of religions (Guthrie, 2015). It seems that we might actually be wired to see life rather than no-life in things by default. In the (critical) words of Tim Ingold:

“Thus we have all evolved to be closet animists without of course realizing it. Intuitive non-animists have been selected out, due to unfortunate encounters with things that turned out to be more alive than anticipated” (Ingold, 2006: 11).

Study on characteristics for animacy in product design

Our hypotheses stated that an artefact featuring characteristics of *animacy* has a higher rating in vocabulary connected to being alive. This was tested for all characteristics individually. Even if seven characteristics were defined to be important for the perception of life in products, only six were tested since *communication* as a very broad and also well-established function in interactive products would have gone beyond the scope of this study.

All tests included pairs of objects, videos or illustrations, which differed in the degree of *animacy*: One (object or video) featured the characteristic to be tested, the other purposefully neglected it. Study participants filled out thirteen different questionnaires. One of these collected personal data like age and gender. The other twelve contained semantic differentials (Osgood, Suci, & Tannenbaum,

Figure 1. The room's setup with pictures of the different areas.

1957), with which the subject rated the objects, videos or images. Semantic differentials were used because of their flexibility, ease of use and because they require little time to be filled out by test persons. The differentials consisted of nine different value pairs, five of which were only distractors that were not analyzed (e.g. extraordinary – ordinary, organic – artificial, active – passive, innovative – traditional, attractive – repulsive). The other four pairs of words related to being alive (animate – inanimate and lively – lifeless) and to character and personality (personal – impersonal and characterful – characterless). Originally, the test was conducted in German but the words were translated for this research paper.

The testing took place on two consecutive days at the Salzburg University of Applied Sciences. Two people worked on this experiment: The test supervisor stayed in the room with the subject, introduced him to the test, used a remote control, handed out and collected the questionnaires (see Figure 1) while the assistant recruited the subjects.

The six tests

Adaptability

This experiment was designed to evaluate a product's ability to adapt to its environment and/or its user by itself. Here, the subject was confronted with nearly

identical looking pieces of foam. He/she was instructed to take the material into the hands to get to know it (see Figure 2). The first one (A) is a special foam that adapts to the pressure with which it is handled and takes the shape of the object which is pressed into it and it keeps it a few moments after the pressure is removed. The second cuboid (B) is made out of normal foam which returns to its original shape immediately.

Energy

To test the impact of a product's acquisition of energy on the perception of that object, two torches were chosen (see Figure 3). The torch on the left has a battery and a simple switch on its side whereas the torch on the right requires the test subject to turn the crank in order to power it. The subject was asked to turn on and rate the torches consecutively.

Figure 2. Setup for testing adaptability.

Figure 3. Three views of torches used to test energy.

Goal-oriented movement

Goal-oriented movement is movement of a product (or a part of the product) unambiguously dedicated to reach a goal. Two videos – inspired by the famous video from Heider and Simmel (1944) – were used. Both videos (see Figure 4 for a screenshot) feature one moving triangle, three moving circles and three non-moving squares. In one scene, the geometrical shapes seem to follow a goal while in another scene they do not. The black-and-white scenes take about 30 seconds.

Memory

An animated product should have the ability to learn and memorize things such as its owner’s habits and preferences. For this experiment the product’s behavior was presented with the help of a photo story, for the simple reason that testing this premise in real time would have been far too time-intensive for this experiment (see Figure 5). Both stories start with the same situation: The alarm clock rings, someone gets up. Then he turns on the coffee machine. He waits until the machine is ready to work. Then the user makes his coffee by starting the process, waiting and then stopping it when the desired amount of coffee is in the cup. Then the next cup is placed under the machine (a smaller one for the partner) and the user starts the process, waits then stops the machine when the desired amount of coffee is in the cup. This is

Figure 4. Screenshot from the video featuring goal-oriented movement.

followed by the statement “one week later”. At this point the stories start to diverge. In the first story the exact same situation as the one described before is shown again.

The second photo story (see Figure 6) starts with an alarm clock but then the situation changes. On the second photo the coffee machine switches itself on. Then the person gets up and pushes the first cup under the coffee machine. The machine recognizes the cup and starts to brew coffee autonomously, regulating the amount of coffee depending on cup size. The user can prepare breakfast while the coffee machine makes his coffee. When the machine is finished the user brings another cup for his partner. The machine again recognizes the cup and makes the coffee all by itself. When finished the machine will turn itself off.

Regeneration

This characteristic addresses the product’s ability to heal or repair itself from small damages – ideally without any help from the user. Regeneration can be

Figure 5. The first part of the photo story used to test memory.

Figure 6. The memory part from the photo story.

introduced to products through their materials. Due to the fact that most self-healing materials are still in development, two videos (see Figure 7) were used to show the effect the self-healing material has. One video shows a material, which gets scratched and stays scratched. The other one shows the very same material, which again gets scratched but this time is able to heal itself.

Sensation

For testing the impact sensation has on the perception of life a simple trick is used. Two similar lamps are placed on one table (see Figure 8). Both of them are plugged in and the subject is told to turn them on. One of them works in a traditional way with a switch to be turned on. The other one “senses” that the subject is near and it turns on by itself. This is accomplished using a remote control operated by the researcher without the subject’s knowledge.

Data analysis and findings

A total of 31 people were tested but a check on the consistency of the answers led to the exclusion of one

subject. The subjects’ (15f, 15m) age ranged from 18 to 42 (mean 24.00 ±5.99 years). The value pairs are rated from -3 to +3 with -3 meaning totally animate/lively/ personal/characterful and +3 meaning completely inanimate/lifeless/impersonal/characterless.

The following section shows the individual analyses for each tested characteristic and for each of the four relevant items.

Adaptability

In the experiment, this was the first tested characteristic. Table 1 shows that all four items show significant differences between the object with and the object without the characteristic adaptability. The standard deviations are quite high for every item.

Energy

The results for energy are similar to those for adaptability (see Table 2), but with a general lower standard deviation for each item. The differences between the two objects are again on a significant level.

Figure 7. Screenshots from the video which features regeneration.

Figure 8. Setup for testing sensation with the lamps used.

Goal-oriented movement

For goal-oriented movement, no significant differences could be found between the two videos for three of the four items (see Table 3). Only the item animate – inanimate was rated significantly different. The standard deviations are again high, especially for the item characterful – characterless.

Memory

The characteristic memory was rated significantly different between the two videos in three of the four items (see Table 4). Only the item characterful/characterless showed no significant difference and has also the highest standard deviation.

Table 1. *t*-test for adaptability (animated object/video vs. unanimated object/video).

Item	Standard Deviation	T	p (two-tailed)
animate – inanimate	2.143	-6.134	.000
lively – lifeless	2.300	-6.032	.000
characterful – characterless	2.463	-4.597	.000
personal – impersonal	2.013	-3.991	.000

Table 2. *t*-test for energy (animated object/video vs. unanimated object/video).

Item	Standard Deviation	T	p (two-tailed)
animate – inanimate	1.964	-7.623	.000
lively – lifeless	1.724	-6.885	.000
characterful – characterless	1.512	-6.158	.000
personal – impersonal	2.025	-4.417	.000

Table 3. *t*-test for goal-oriented movement (animated object/video vs. unanimated object/video).

Item	Standard Deviation	T	p (two-tailed)
animate – inanimate	1.771	2.989	.006
lively – lifeless	2.096	1.481	.149
characterful – characterless	2.143	-1.022	.315
personal – impersonal	2.825	0.905	.373

Table 4. *t*-test for memory/learning (animated object/video vs. unanimated object/video).

Item	Standard Deviation	T	p (two-tailed)
animate – inanimate	2.493	-4.761	.000
lively – lifeless	2.449	-5.070	.000
characterful – characterless	4.025	-1.270	.214
personal – impersonal	2.662	-3.018	.005

Figure 9. Rating for the four items for the objects featuring the characteristics.

Regeneration

Two of the four items (animate/inanimate and lively/lifeless) were rated significantly different between the two videos (see Table 5). The standard deviation for all items is quite moderate.

Sensation

All items for sensation prove a significant difference between the animated and the unanimated objects (see Table 6) with moderate standard deviations.

Looking at the overall findings, we created graphic profiles for the semantic differentials by evaluating the mean for each value pair and connecting the means with lines. Figure 9 shows this data for the animated objects/videos.

Figure 10 shows the ratings for the unanimated objects or videos. It is visible that the items were generally ranked with higher values. An exemption is the characteristic goal-oriented movement, which has remarkably low values for the items animate – inanimate, lively – lifeless and characterful – characterless.

To test our hypotheses we also did a two-tailed t-test for each characteristic and compared the ratings of the (averaged) four items between the animated and the unanimated object or video (see Table 7). The characteristic goal-oriented movement is the only one that shows no significant difference between the two videos. As a reminder, this characteristic was represented by a different behavior of geometrical objects.

The overall outcome of our statistical analyses confirms our hypotheses for five of six characteristics: adaptability, energy, memory, regeneration and sensation. The correspondent hypothesis for goal-oriented movement had to be rejected.

Interpretation and further observations

When asked, after finishing the tests, where they had experienced difficulties, three of the subjects mentioned rating qualities connecting to *animacy* (animate and lively) but the others had no problem related to these. Seven subjects thought rating organically – artificial (one of the distractor items) was especially difficult because all of the objects/videos were artificial. Seven subjects mentioned active – passive as

Table 5. t-test for regeneration (animated object/video vs. unanimated object/video).

Item	Standard Deviation	T	p (two-tailed)
animate – inanimate	2.638	-4.014	.000
lively – lifeless	2.173	-5.965	.000
characterful – characterless	1.929	-0.189	.851
personal – impersonal	2.542	-1.736	.093

Table 6. t-test for sensation (animated object/video vs. unanimated object/video).

Item	Standard Deviation	T	p (two-tailed)
animate – inanimate	1.960	-9.037	.000
lively – lifeless	1.889	-10.052	.000
characterful – characterless	2.636	-2.355	.025
personal – impersonal	1.964	-5.392	.000

Figure 10. Rating for the four items for the objects not featuring the characteristics.

especially difficult to rate because, even if the instruction told them to rate the objects, some were not sure if they had to rate if the user (not the object) was active/passive or the object. Further, one person mentioned attractive – repulsive, personal – impersonal and innovative – traditional as difficult to rate.

Only the characteristic – goal-oriented movement – did not lead to a higher ranking of the vocabulary connected to being alive. An explanation for this might be that there is a little bit more movement in the not goal-oriented video than in the other one and each pentagon moves in a unique way. This, and especially the good rating of the video not featuring goal-oriented movement, could indicate that movement has an influence on the perception of life but it does not have to be goal-oriented. Additionally, it may not have been the right decision to ask the subjects to rate the whole sequence. The outcomes could be different if the instruction was to rate just the triangle. One participant mentioned that he perceived some kind of goal in both videos. He stated that the triangular in the first video is nice because it cares for the pentagons in some way. On the other hand he perceived the triangular in the second video as unfriendly. He stated that it came in and laid into the pentagons.

One subject stated that he perceived the coffee machine featuring memory/learning, the video featuring regeneration and the lamp featuring

Table 7. *t*-test for the characteristics.

Characteristic	t	p (two-tailed)
adaptability	-6.190	.000
energy	-8.955	.000
goal-oriented movement	1.346	.189
memory	-3.899	.001
regeneration	-4.463	.000
sensation	-8.403	.000

sensation as less personal than the regular ones. When looking at the mean ratings this statement was not proved right for the majority of the subjects.

For designers, these findings show that the characteristic here labeled as *animacy* can actually be injected into products. We see the use of regenerative materials and the addition of adaptive and interactive features as strong candidates for a new design process.

Conclusion: Designing for animism

The idea of designed animism actually dates back to the 1970s when design theorist treated the impact of pervasive computing on the human experience and design as a discipline (Laurel, 2003). Of late, approaches in design research have been steered towards purposely increasing emotional durability of products through design. As shown in a recent conference paper, *animism* can actually be used as an appropriate design metaphor for interactive design (Van Allen, McVeigh-Schultz, Brown, Kim, & Lara, 2013). Not all types of design share such intrinsic relationships with *animism*, but all would arguably benefit from the ongoing discussion of a new animism.

Additional research on the evolutionary accuracy of *animacy* is needed to address whether or not *animacy* is innate. Evolutionary psychology, as an explanatory framework could prove fruitful for approaching an answer.

Is *animism* something to be encouraged or renounced for society to work? The evolutionary process is not teleological and, as Popper remarked, “the future is open”. “Thus it is our duty, not to prophesy evil, but, rather, to fight for a better world,” he added (Popper, 1967). It is argued here that there can only be a better world with better design solutions. It is safe to say that humans have a deeply ingrained fascination with stuff, which has become a serious concern when considering the resources required making all such stuff. Animism, understood as a deeply rooted understanding of a world unfolding, alive with things could very well lead to a more sustainable future. Is it

possible that we have come so removed from the creation of the objects around us that we have dropped all parenthood-like affection? Industrialization and in a sense industrial design have removed the production of things by one degree creating a system where things are mothered by things. Further research might address any correlation between the Cartesian dualism and the Industrial era.

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Beyond Death: Using design to transcend life, memories and traditions

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Abstract Sustainable design provides benefits across a product's lifecycle, particularly for end of life. Designers and end users are aware that as much as product lifetime can be extended, no artifact can last forever. But when looking at end of life in human beings, most people are not comfortable with dealing with death whether is their own or of someone else's. Sustainability can provide initial strategies for designing for human death but in order to make a significant contribution to this area, designers need to address a wider set of needs that also include social, emotional and psychological issues. Models such as Maslow's hierarchy of human needs can provide a good framework for identifying the necessary dimensions that involve designing for death. This paper describes design strategies that align with Maslow's list of needs and uses design projects from industry and academia as examples of how to apply them. The objective of presenting these ideas and case studies is to generate awareness and discussion in an important area of design that is sometimes overlooked. Death is imminent for all human beings and design has the ability of removing pain, anxiety and fear that is often associated with it.

Keywords *Design, Death, Life, Emotion, Sustainability*

Introduction

The prevalence of sustainability in design practice provides a deep understanding of the lifecycle in manufactured goods. This understanding leads to design decisions that minimize environmental impact particularly for end of life (Gehin et al, 2008). Strategies such as materials selection, design for disassembly, repurposing and recyclability, all provide effective alternatives for disposing of an artifact once is no longer functional or needed. Designing for end of life of living beings, however, is significantly more challenging and unclear. Death is a topic that is hard to assimilate for most individuals and many cultures avoid talking about it unless absolutely necessary (Lee, 2008). Sustainable design can provide a base framework for envisioning death as an imminent step in the lifecycle, whether applied to objects or to people. As death is imminent for every living being, it needs to be planned for. However, addressing death as a simple step in the lifecycle is not enough to address the complex needs that people have when facing death-related issues. Multi-dimensional models of human needs such as Maslow's hierarchy of needs provides an integrated view of elements that need to be addressed for human end of life, which normally involve issues around emotions, love, safety, traditions, and physical wellbeing, among others.

Current efforts in design for death integrate strategies such as increased human interaction during illness, planning of death, traditions for funerals and burials, enabling lasting memories of people who are no longer alive and objects that reflect the impact that someone's life had in society. A series of examples of commercial products and academic projects provide ways of

addressing emotional and practical needs of people who are dying as well as their loved ones. This paper aims at generating awareness and discussion in this area so that designers can be mindful of how their designs can improve experiences in extreme situations such as end of life. By working in this important design category, designers also have the opportunity to reflect on the impact that their personal work can have in society when their designs help people facing difficult situations as well as promote cultural change for generations to come.

End of life in product design

A key strategy in sustainable design whenever developing new concepts is to pay attention to all steps in the lifecycle, from fabrication to distribution and use, to end of life. Awareness of these stages allows designers to anticipate consequences derived from potential features and to make decisions that minimize environmental impact. The result of this process is products with longer useful lives that are easier to repair and upgrade. Once their inevitable end of life arrives they also are easier to dispose of, recycle or repurpose. These benefits add value to products and make them more appealing to users and to the environment (Lobos & Babbitt, 2013).

As designers embrace whole lifecycle thinking, they become familiar with accepting death as part of any product's cycle. Death is an inevitable step of the natural cycle that nevertheless opens up space for new life to emerge and thrive. Every designed artifact will go through a natural flow of turning from something useful into something no longer needed (McDonough & Braungart, 2002). Commonly known as end-of-life,

Figure 1. List of strategies for Design for Death according to Maslow's hierarchy of Needs.

designers need to be aware of its implications and design products around it. Whether by product wear, failure, or in other unfortunate cases, by planned obsolescence, products cannot last forever and will stop being useful or functional at some point.

Understanding human end of life

End of life in human-made objects is expected and in most cases, easily accepted. As much as consumers hate to have their favorite products break down, they are used in general to having to replace objects that no longer meet their needs. However, when thinking of end of life in living things, most people have a hard time accepting death, even if deep down they know that is unavoidable. Death in most cultures is a hard concept to assimilate and people struggle when dealing with the death of others around them, not to mention their own. People who lose someone that they care about frequently go through periods of anxiety and denial before they begin to accept their death (Kastenbaum, 2012) as part of a mourning period which can be painful, disruptive and detrimental for their own wellbeing. Methods for confronting end of life range from practical to spiritual. After people die their body needs to be disposed of in a safe and respectful way and it is common to have a public memorial ceremony of some sort, where the life of the person is honored and remembered. These ceremonies seem to be an important step in the mourning process that involves accepting the passing of a loved one (Hanington, 2004).

Design can play a big role in helping people go through the painful moments around death. It is during moments like these where design's empathetic approach becomes more useful. In a recent article from UK's Design Council about design for death, critic Alice Rawsthorn describes how a designer's ability of "analysing the strengths and weaknesses of present systems and rituals with an open mind, and applying grace, foresight, rigour, sensitivity and imagination to envisaging better outcomes could help us to die more humanely" (qtd. in Pallister, 2015). There is a growing interest across various communities of making death a topic that is discussed more openly and directly. Our Common Practice (<http://ourcommonpractice.com/>), a Philadelphia-based company that works with hospital and healthcare organizations, facilitates discussions about death among healthcare professionals and patients in order to reduce uncertainty and anxiety around the topic. Modern Loss (<http://modernloss.com/>) is an online network that brings people together to talk about loss, grief and death. Wake Up to Dying Project (<http://www.wakeuptodyingproject.org/>) is an organization that collects writings and stories about death, dying and life. At the academic level, several institutions such as University of Glasgow, University of Cambridge and Royal College of Art have research centers that include design for end of life in their project lists. Drexel University has offered a course named "It's a Beautiful Life." Led by professor Kenneth Bingham, the writing course matches students with terminal patients at a local hospice, enabling a space where students can learn more about end of life and interact with people in who are dying. The industrial design graduate program at Rochester Institute of Technology (RIT) recently developed a project led by the author named "Design your Death" where students developed concepts that improved situations around death. One of the first exercises that students in this course did was to write their own obituary, which helped them in reflecting on the impact that they wanted to have as individuals and as designers. The examples mentioned above are just a small sample of the work that is being generated for improving death-related issues. An important element that all of these initiatives have in common is that they open up discussions about death as a way of accepting it and enabling more fulfilling lives. Going through their stories, projects and testimonials makes it evident that their focus is not to look at death as a dark, morbid event but rather as an opportunity for living to the fullest, regardless of the amount of time that people have ahead of them.

Key elements in design for death

The apparent complexity of design for death might be simplified by identifying key areas that need to be addressed. By taking Maslow's hierarchy of needs as point of reference, it is possible to categorize strategies that build up from basic tangible needs for survival up to more more complex, psychological ones (Figure 1).

When looking at products out in the marketplace that make death more approachable, it is possible to align them with the categories mentioned above. It is important to understand that products that address only a limited number of categories are not as effective as those that take a more holistic approach and integrate multiple dimensions of needs. Case in point, After I Go, an app concept developed by Paul Bennett, creative director at IDEO, for entrepreneur Paul Gaffney. The app was originally envisioned as something very simple and pragmatic that would help someone in making end of life decisions such as drafting a will, choosing preferences for a funeral or even leaving account passwords accessible to designated people (Mooallem, 2015), all of which would fall into the physiological and safety layers of the hierarchy structure. The app had a lukewarm reception by potential consumers and a newer version was developed to include emotional elements such as recorded messages, pictures, and memories of significant events. This is when the app started to receive a lot of attention from the public and from the press although it was eventually abandoned by Gaffney, who moved to other projects. After I Go is still a good example of how complex the notion of death is to people. As much as we can make connections

Figure 2. Palliative care bathing glove. Photo by Yi Feng.

between burial practices and their effect on the environment, we also have to pay attention to aspects that create strong feelings and emotions. Most successful products in the market follow the idea of offering multiple benefits at different levels. If a product is attractive but not durable, for example, it will not be embraced by the user, just like a product that might work very well but is too bulky might become too expensive to commercialize. Products that provide benefits at multiple layers tend to be more effective over time, which increases their potential sustainability (Lobos, 2014). In the case of design for death, the same principle applies, where based on the Hierarchy of Needs, most users need to fulfill needs at multiple levels. Below is a breakdown of Maslow's needs as applied to design for death, which include examples of products that illustrate how these needs can be addressed.

Painless death

The healthcare industry has identified the need for improving the way that treatments and patient wellbeing are being addressed. While medically there are many methods that produce efficient results and increase successful outcome of treatments, the logistics around patient care, particularly in terms of administrative and legal implications has created a colder environment that provides patients with the physical help they need but does not take into account their emotional wellbeing (Stacey et al., 2011). Palliative care is a good example of a healthcare philosophy that pays attention to physical, emotional and even spiritual needs. Used primarily for patients with serious, sometimes terminal issues, as well as for their families, palliative care uses methods that relieve painful symptoms and uncomfortable procedures (Sepúlveda et al., 2002). For terminal patients, receiving palliative care can make the difference between being able to come to terms with their end of life and to enjoy their final days with rewarding activities and loved ones versus being tormented with

Figure 3. Tikker watch. Image by Tom Townsend. Licensed under CC BY 2.0. Retrieved from: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/brizzlebornandbred/15243431197>

disruptive treatments that do little to extend their life but end up decreasing its quality. Yi Feng, graduate student in industrial design at RIT, developed a bathing glove concept that makes patient care more caring and less institutional (Figure 2). Feng noticed that when giving baths to patients, nurses tend to use towels folded several times, which disposed of several times during a bath and replaced with clean ones. This practice creates a physical separation between the caregiver and the patient, not to mention large amounts of dirty laundry. Feng's design concept works more like a semi-open glove that provides the caregiver with more control for cleaning and also feels more connected to the patient. Subtle symbols like being able to get a bit closer to someone can make a big difference, particularly in difficult circumstances or when going through an illness.

Planning for death

Death is a delicate topic that most people prefer to ignore until absolutely necessary. It's ironic that one of the few things in life that is absolutely certain is also one of the least discussed. A common design approach for enabling conversations around death is not to address it directly but rather to highlight elements around it that make people more conscious of their mortality and the consequences that come along with it. Tikker is a wristwatch that reminds users of their limited life in a passive way (Figure 3). Tikker is currently out in the market, available from vendors like Amazon as well as through its own website <http://mytikker.com/>.

The watch measures time in two ways: The first one is the traditional way, telling the user actual time. The second one is a countdown timer set accordingly to the user's birthdate and life expectancy. As the user wears the watch he or she is reminded of how much time is left before a projected death. The goal of the

Figure 4. SoulSpace. Photo by Akanksha Vishwakarma.

watch is to make users mindful of how finite their time on earth is, encouraging them to engage in more meaningful activities. Akanksha Vishwakarma at RIT developed SoulSpace, a concept board game that makes people aware of their material possessions and how they might be distributed after their death (Figure 4).

Disputes over distribution of material possessions are common after someone dies and many families quarrel over this issue. The goal of SoulSpace is to use a neutral environment, in this case astronomy, in which characters in the game explore the different types of value that their possessions might have and identify ways of distributing them. While playing the game, users realize that the value of material possessions is not merely economical. Although some possessions have high monetary value other ones have sentimental or practical value. Tikker and SoulSpace are examples of products that bring up delicate topics, making their users more conscious of how they live their lives and of decisions that they should make before they are gone for good.

Michael Kelly, also a graduate design student at RIT, took an entirely different approach on designing for death. United States is suffering of an increased number of school shootings, which are causing countless deaths of innocent people and leave thousands others traumatized by the horrific acts. There has been significant discussion on why these acts of violence are so prevalent in U.S. society but there are many challenges in preventing them from continue happening. Kelly decided to connect school shootings with the project from the angle of someone facing their potential death and having to defend their life and perhaps even the life of others. In early stages of the project Kelly explored ways of fighting back a mass shooter but ended up avoiding the use of violence to prevent violence, focusing instead on providing safety. The solution is a desk workstation with a removable top made out of ultra-high molecular polyethylene, a lightweight, inexpensive, impact-resistant material. In case of an emergency, the top can be removed quickly and be used as a shield (Figure 5).

Other potential uses for the desk include providing shelter from natural catastrophes such as earthquakes and the ability to use the top as display frame for

Figure 5. Bullet-resistant desk. Photo by Michael Kelly.

activities during class. While these additional uses are appreciated, the fact that a product of this kind needs to exist in today's U.S. educational system remains a fact very hard to assimilate. Kelly's desk concept provides another dimension to the power of design, which not only provides practical solutions to delicate problems but also serves as platform for generating dialog and awareness around sensitive issues.

Traditions and funerals

Death is filled with rich traditions and ceremonies that vary between cultures. Depending on different beliefs, some people see it as the last point of an endless cycle of life, while others see it as a transition to a different dimension, and some people see it as the absolute end of existence (Gire, 2014). The impact that death has in societies is extremely important and the way that funerals are performed is full of rich symbols and traditions. RIT student Hui-Yu Yang analyzed how people in China are expected to visit the graves of their ancestors but newer generations don't feel as inclined to follow this tradition due to long distances that have to be travelled or simple lack of connection to the deceased relative. Yang envisioned a small plant pot that comes in geometric or organic shapes, and is given to a person that recently lost a relative (Figure 6). The person takes care of the plant for a couple of months in preparation for bringing it to the graveyard as an offering. This action of taking care of a plant makes an emotional connection between the person's daily activities and the memory of the deceased relative that will be visited. This experience provides more purpose to the visit to the graveyard so that the person feels more inclined to make the trip and successfully deliver the plant.

Sustainability awareness is becoming more prevalent in burial practices. While burials provide friends and relatives of a deceased person the feeling that he or she is going to a good place, actual details on how people are buried have gone from essential to highly symbolic and even lavish. Coffins are more than

Figure 6. Stone Pots. Photo by Hui-yu Yang.

containers that in help in transporting a body, providing also the perception of preservation and reflect the interests of the deceased person (Hanington, 2004), and in many cases, their economical and social status. The use of coffins as status symbols is not new. Burials for Egyptian and Mayan kings were extremely elaborate, for example, involving the construction of grandiose pyramids and temples, some of this are considered architectural masterpieces of the human race. Besides their symbolic importance, coffins and caskets also generate important environmental issues, one of them being materials used in their fabrication that do not degrade easily when buried and even generate toxic materials that ruin the soil. Known as the “green burial movement”, this trend involves simple burial ceremonies and caskets made out of natural materials. The goal of this movement is to minimize the economical and environmental impact of burials while allowing people to focus on honoring the memory of the person who has departed. Some designs are going even a step further and making a literal connection between mortal remains and nature. Pierre Rivière and Enzo Pascual designed Emergence, a biodegradable coffin concept that includes tree seeds inside (Figure 7). Once the coffin is buried the materials in the coffin along with the body and the seeds will germinate into a living tree. Emergence earned first place at the Design for Death competition organized by Design Boom in 2013.

RIT student Elizabeth Stegner wanted to explore simple casket design that paid strong attention to materials selection. Her design concept named Cocoon uses ebonizing molded cardboard, which provides enough structural integrity during a funeral and burial but once is in contact with the soil it degrades easily (Figure 8). Another element that Stegner explored as a formal language that was accepted by a wider segment of users. While sustainable burials are gaining popularity, people still perceive them as geared towards environmentalists. Cocoon tries to find a balance between finding a casket that is simple but still acceptable for mainstream funerals. Cocoon’s form shows a clean and elegant approach to the traditionally more ornate casket but maintains an elegance that is appreciated when burying a loved one.

Lasting memories

People who loose someone important in their lives have a hard time accepting his/her departure. A mourning process, which can last from a few days to

Figure 7. Emergence coffin concept. Image by PR and EP. Licensed under CC BY 4.0. Retrieved from: http://www.designboom.com/wp-content/compsub/372330/2013-04-17/img_2_1366171612_9b3970af296f99894509776ddd9cd4ef.jpg

several years, is a time where people acknowledge that their life can continue without the presence of someone close to them who seized to exist (Gire, 2014). As part of the mourning process people look for ways of keeping alive the memory of their loved ones and seek out symbols that suggest that life does not end when someone dies but that it rather takes another form. There is an increasing number of designs that use plants as a way of symbolizing the generation of new life that comes from previously living organisms turning into nutrients that generate new life. RIT student Wilson ‘Spar’ Patton was interested in developing a keepsake for funeral services that provided the opportunity to extend the memory of the person who recently died. Patton was interested in the simple, yet common tradition of giving away seeds or little trees at funeral services so that people plant them when returning home. After a few iterations that went from shovel-like planters to jewelry boxes, Patton’s final design concept is a small round vessel named Heart Tender. Made out of peat-based plaster, the design is easy to transport, display and store and it can also be planted as it contains seeds that will germinate and turn into new plants (Figure 9).

For Patton it was important to address key moments that people go through during and after a funeral so that this vessel wouldn’t feel out of place. Several stages of product interaction were carefully considered so that people had enough flexibility to do with the box whatever they felt would make more sense for keeping the memory of a loved one alive. From a small, round shape that can be put in a shirt’s pocket to an attractive, neutral appearance that could look good on top of a mantel to materials that would degrade easily if people decided to plant it, all of these features go back to how people can keep someone’s memory alive. Heart Tender’s shape is also result of experimenting with the peat plaster in order to find shapes that were molded easily and that wouldn’t crumble away while handling them. The result is a simple but effective symbol that leads to the creation of new life. This is an innate ability that designers

Figure 8. Sustainable coffin. Photo by Elizabeth Stegner.

have, one where topics laced with fear such as death can be transformed into joyful moments that endure (Pallister, 2015).

Impact and legacy

Humans have a hard time accepting that their life is finite and limited and that they might soon be forgotten. Fear of death makes people think of ways of extending their lives for as long as possible, whether by maintaining a healthier lifestyle or by finding ways of leaving their mark on earth. Leaving an important legacy for future generations is a consequence of resisting death but it becomes less important once someone acknowledges their imminent departure. Research in the impact of death awareness in everyday life shows that when people become more aware of their mortality their value of the present increases while their value of the future diminishes (Kelley and Schmeichel, 2015). People who confront their own mortality tend to enjoy life more because they want to maximize their time on earth. It is not necessarily about doing something that will transform the world such as finding a cure for a devastating disease, proving a radical scientific theory of leaving large amounts of money; in most cases is about having a fulfilling life, day after day. This appreciation of life can also be connected with common behaviors around scarcity, where people who realize that something is

Figure 10. Rememberance digital photo frame. Photo by Reema Al-Dosari.

Figure 9. Heart Tender at multiple stages of use. Photo by William Patton.

not permanent or abundant will value it more (King et al, 2009). It is in cases like this where products like Tikker become powerful tools for raising the relevance that mindful daily activities have in achieving fulfilling life. Something as simple as imagining the present year as the last year that someone might live will encourage them to reach out to friends that they haven't connected in a while or to do engage in more social activities (Brooks, 2016).

Just as designers' awareness of the natural cycle of their products helps them in developing solutions that are more sustainable, being conscious of their own mortality and the one of those that they design for can be significantly helpful when designing for death. From looking at the way that people across different cultures responds to death it is clear that they want to make sure that their life has meaning and that their time on earth has had impact on society and the environment. RIT student Reema Al-Dosari developed a digital frame concept named "Rememberance" that integrates memory and tradition (Figure 10). By focusing on traditional geometric patterns the frame creates a collage where family pictures are displayed in different layouts. The frame can be hung from the wall, rest on a surface or be held like a traditional photo album. The result is a collection of images that connect with family, tradition and even a home's décor. By having objects that keep important memories alive, people can have more meaningful lives and be more conscious of the activities that they are involved in. Designed goods have the potential to go beyond just being stuff that gets lots in a sea of material possessions, improving quality of life at physical, mental and spiritual levels.

Conclusions

Integrating design and death provides important benefits to the education and practice of the profession, ranging from developing new skills on what seems to be a challenging topic to helping people through hard moments and decisions, to discovering deeper roles for designers as shapers of culture. Based on the benefits of product lifetime awareness, designers can be just as reflective on their own

mortality as well as the mortality of those who they design for. Death is a natural and inevitable step of every living thing, yet many cultures have a hard time dealing with it. As much as people try to ignore it, sooner or later they will be faced with complications in life that could have been minimized had they been addressed in time. Efforts in the healthcare industry such as palliative care provide patients with better treatments that benefit physical, mental and emotional wellbeing.

Design has the ability of validating someone's life as well as perpetuating it in a meaningful way. In the case of the academic project of designing someone's own death, lead by the author, it was evident that as students developed their projects they became conscious of the type of emotions that they wanted to generate in their users. They carefully explored different types of elements, materials, symbols, experiences, forms, and other components, in order to fully capture the essence of how people wanted to live, die and be remembered. Students quickly identified how important death is to every culture in the world and how diverse the way of dealing with it is. Given that the group of students and faculty was highly diverse and represented people from China, Taiwan, Saudi Arabia, India, United States and Latin America, it was possible to discover new traditions and to make interesting connections on how death is perceived across different cultures and geographies.

An important finding of this body of work is the effect that open discussions about death have in someone's life. People tend to be uncomfortable talking about this topic and have a hard time accepting that life is finite. However, being aware of that mortality seems to remove a burden from a lot of people and encourages them to pursue a more active and fulfilling life. It also seems to reduce the pressure of achieving extraordinary things in life, focusing instead on appreciating simple things in everyday life. The ability that designers have to approach complex problems with an open mind and empathy is a key component for improving issues around death. Just like traditional design problems deal with functional, aesthetic and experiential issues, death is a multi-layered system that needs to be addressed from multiple angles simultaneously. Using models that cover physical, mental and emotional human needs.

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Introducing Graphic Experiential Evidencing (GEE). How can the use of graphic novel fill a gap in the service design toolkit for communicating experience and emotion?

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Abstract With an increasing focus on experience-centric services, where deeper customer connection is to be achieved by heightened dramaturgy and emotional engagement, service design must ensure it has tools that can model and communicate these experiences during service development.

Existing methods of visualizing services such as the Service Blueprint, whilst good for modeling the structure of experience delivery, do not convey the richness of the experiences itself.

Graphic Experiential Evidencing (GEE) has been developed through a process of research by design during a design intervention for the improvement of stadium football experience, when existing service design visualization tools were found lacking for the communicating of the designed experience to stakeholders.

This paper describes work in progress that adapts the graphic novel as a way to aid in the conveying of desired 'on brand' experience and desired emotional response in context.

Interviews with those involved in the project as well as other service designers suggest that using GEE in combination with existing service design tools offers great promise. Results show that the technique gives the service designer new ways to deliver an experience sample and communicate projected experiences and emotion to clients during the development of new services.

Keywords *Service design, Visualization, Graphic novel, Experience, Evidencing*

Introduction

Suri (2004) quotes Moggeridge's well-known tautology 'The only way to experience an experience is by experiencing it'. She uses it as a way to underline the need for designers to use their visual skills and design tools not just as a way to convey insights and findings but in a fuller more experiential way for 'Developing common vision.....Creating richer representation.' (Suri, 2004, p. 16)

If Service Design is the design of experience (LiveWork, 2008) then we need to ensure that we have tools that can develop a common vision of the desired experience rather than just that of the system of delivery. Whilst companies are increasingly putting customer experience at the core of their service offerings (Haeckel, Carbone, & Berry, 2003; Pine & Gilmore, 1999; Voss, Roth, & Chase, 2008), the real

power of design is making the experience more tangible during the design process itself (Suri, 2004).

Service designers use visualization during all stages of the service design process. This paper focuses on the generative phase. This paper is authored by the service designer who developed the technique.

Paper structure

The paper opens with an overview of service design visualization, showing a gap in the disciplines 'toolkit' and briefly introduces the use of cartoons and the emotional response to the drawn image. It describes the context of GEE's introduction, insight into the technique and some examples. Then described is the method and the framework of analysis. The paper closes with a discussion and further work followed a conclusion.

Figure 1. (Halvorsrud et al., 2014).

Background

Service designers use visualization to make services more tangible (Kimbell, 2009; Segelström & Holmlid, 2011) and easier to communicate (Segelström, 2009), using such tools at the start of the process to visualize the existing service and to quickly sketch potential improvements and new artifacts.

The two main visualization tools for service modeling; Customer Journey Map and the Service Blueprint does not express detailed experiential outcome from interaction with the service (Won, Ko, Im, & Park, 2013), rather visualizing the structure of the service. The Service Experience Blueprint attempts to manage the experience across multi-interfaces (Patrício, Fisk, & e Cunha, 2008) but again is not intended to detail the experience itself. More recent work by Halvorsrud, Lee, Haugstveit & Følstad (2014) attempts to find a common language for communicating touchpoints within the customer journey modeling tradition.

Where this offers a standardized language of communication it does not address any deep contextual or emotional experience of the service moment.

Clatworthy, Fjuk, Kvale, & Matthews (2015) bring more expression to customers emotional response to touchpoints in the customer journey, beyond the happy-sad dichotomy to introduce precise mood words to describe the experience. What this work lacks however is the experiential detail of the service moment alluded to by Won et al (2013).

The use of storyboard is common across many fields of design (Curedale, 2013; Meroni & Sangiorgi, 2011). Adapted from the film industry (Curedale, 2013; Meroni & Sangiorgi, 2011; Segelström, 2010) the storyboard acts as a script and like the customer journey shows the flow of the action over time, however in a pictorial fashion. It puts focus on the interactions and touch points. The storyboard can express more detail than the customer journey, communicating the style of the service as well as bring focus to specific touchpoints and elements in context (Meroni & Sangiorgi, 2011). The storyboard can be constructed in many media from simple sketches, to photomontage to other realistic visual representations (Meroni & Sangiorgi, 2011; Tassi, 2009). This may offer a glimpse of the experience, however it can be argued that the storyboard in many of its manifestations does not have the primary aim to

affect the viewer emotionally.

Evidencing as a service design technique can also offer some contextual detailing that can deliver to an extent a richer representation of a proposed service experience than the tools discussed so far. The technique warrants further attention from the academic community, though it is briefly alluded to by Kimbel (2009) and Suri (2004) if not mentioned directly. With much of the discussion taking place in the design blogosphere it is often used as Kimbell (2009) suggest as a way to describe the reaction to the introduction to a new service. However as Clatworthy (2008) shows when discussing his work with LiveWork, evidencing is used to give a sense of the experience of touchpoints in use. It does this by mocking up touchpoints and placing them in context. In this way it is able to include 'branding elements, design elements, interaction elements and behavioural elements' (Clatworthy, 2008). What evidencing in general doesn't expand on is the dramaturgy of the experience or a projected emotional response.

Though not visualization, other forms of service prototyping include service run-throughs and re-enactment. But as Blomkvist and Holmlid (2010) suggest that these forms techniques can lack authenticity. Furthermore due to the performative nature of service enactments, like the services they represent, they 'cannot be stored' (Zeithaml, Parasuraman, & Berry, 1985, p. 34) which makes them difficult to convey to those not present during the actual role-play.

Using cartoons

Clatworthy (2013) blogs that cartoons are currently being used as part of the visualization tool kit of service design to communicate service concepts as a way to communicate usage and to give guidance. He goes on to raise the point that the way product designers have drawn prototypes, especially concept cars, do it in such a way to caricature products to make them look more desirable. What the renderer does is 'simplify the reality of the object and turn up on the desire of the object itself' (Clatworthy, 2013).

The definitive description of the use, construction and power of the cartoon media can be found in McCloud's book 'Understanding comics' from 1993. McCloud highlights the difficulty of a definitive definition of the nature of the comic or graphic novel but lands for ease of use on 'Sequential Art' after Will Eisner. However

what McCloud points out, is that one of the skill of the graphic artist is to communicate with minimum elements and through the power of the drawings. This moves the technique beyond a reliance on a storyboard approach to communicate the narrative but to expressing the same through as few panels as possible. McCloud also argues that the graphic novel form achieves amplification of meaning through the simplification of the image. Here the medium allows us to focus our attention on the idea and through stripping down, deliver a form of intensity in a similar argument to Clatworthy. As part of the same argument McCloud then shows that this visual stripping down in expressing the experience of the protagonist in any story actually 'allows the reader to mask themselves in a character and safely enter a sensually stimulating world' (McCloud, 1993, p. 43). In this way the viewer can 'be' more than just 'see'.

This leads to the question of how a similar or relatedly appropriate technique might offer renderings of service moments that 'turn up' a sense of the experience and emotional, for the viewer to 'feel' the experience more. This is reinforced when we consider the neuroesthetics based argument of Freedberg and Gallese (2007), that suggests that the 'power of images' generate feelings of emotion and empathy that deliver 'a sense of inward imitation' (Freedberg & Gallese, 2007, p. 197) from the viewer, a mirroring of the emotion expressed in the image.

Context

Graphic Experiential Evidencing (GEE) was developed as a way to express experiences, in some cases the emotional response, the atmosphere of the service moment and when appropriate including touchpoints, as part of the project 'Alt for Norge'. A collaboration between the Oslo School of Architecture and Design and the Norwegian Football Association. As part of the

process it utilized many of the standard service design visualization tools mentioned above as ways to capture customer journeys and to convey insights from fans, stakeholders and designers. However when it came to the conveying the experience of meaningful service moments to decision makers, stakeholders and staff who were not directly involved in the project development, current visualization tools seemed lacking in representing the richness of the experience. To this end experiments using graphic novel were done to help in this communication where they were used in combination with these tools.

The technique

The technique became a negotiation between the vision of the service designer and that of the cartoonist. The style of the work was additionally informed by the organizations new brand values and esthetic.

This negotiation followed the following structure:

1. Understanding the service landscape and experiential goals
2. Sketching with the brand esthetics
3. Scripting by the service designer for the cartoonist
4. Preliminary sketching
5. Adjustment with further scripting
6. Final detailing and finished drawing

1. Understanding the service landscape and experiential goals

Time was taken at the start of the process between the service designer and the cartoonist to understand the goals of the project, the dramaturgy of the service journey and the experience that was being designed for. Comparative experiences were used to give a sense of the tone that was being looked for. These were things such as National day celebrations, being called

Table 1. Summary of Service Design visualisation and modelling tools.

Tool	What it is	Technique employed
Customer Journey	A modeling tool that visualizes time and the points of contact the customer has with the service provider at different touchpoints plotted chronologically along a line. Used for mapping existing services and for developing and communicating new ones.	Visualized as a two dimensional piece. Predominantly using symbols to denote touchpoints. Can include a customer emotion curve.
Service Blueprint	A modeling tool that visualizes the management of the service experience over time. It incorporates elements such as touchpoints but also front and back office staff roles. Used for orchestrating elements of new services.	Visualized as a two dimensional piece showing the layers of people, space and technology management
Emotion Cards	A pack of 12 double sided cards with positive emotional states on one side and the opposite emotion on the back. Used for understanding existing and projected customer emotions.	Printed on cards they are placed on the customer journey at specific touchpoints to express emotional responses.
Story Board	A modeling tool that shows the flow of the action over time in a pictorial fashion. It puts focus on the interactions and touchpoints in context	A two dimensional piece using photomontage and drawings
Evidencing	A tool that visualizes how the service might be or the response to the service if delivered.	Often a photograph incorporating elements or responses to the service, it might also be a mock up of a digital touchpoint
Service enactment	Not strictly visualization but an enactment of the proposed service to give a direct experience even if it is as such a sketch	Acting using makeshift props for touchpoints.

Figure 2. The call to Adventure. Illustration Syver Lauritzen.

up to serve your country, emotive scenes in films.

The service journey was divided into a series of situated meaningful service moments. The cartoonist's task was to visualize these moments. There was some discussion about whether they would be individual panels or multiple panels for story telling also whether there should be speech bubbles or discourse boxes. However these issues were solved as the process went along, responding to the need of the visualization.

2. Sketching with the brand esthetics

Test visualizations were created to interpret the brand style into that of a graphic novel style. The brand values are Ferocity, Solidarity and Pride. Within the graphic novel genre the ferocity value was easiest to portray eventually settling on a style with a Frank Miller feel, which could be described as dark, robust and moody.

Pride and solidarity values could be expressed more easily through that which was being visualized.

3. Scripting by the service designer for the cartoonist

Service moments descriptions were sent to the cartoonist, including their purpose, the type of experience being designed for, touchpoints being shown. It was discovered that this was best achieved when written as a short piece of dramatized fiction.

4. Preliminary sketching

From here the cartoonist offered a sketch of the service moment. Here a negotiation took place between the service designer and the cartoonist about which elements functioned in regards to the service designer's vision, what needed to be conveyed and which elements should be adjusted.

5. Final detailing and finish

Agreed adjustments were then made and final cartoon delivered in digital form.

Figure 3. The call up. Illustration Syver Lauritzen.

The images

In all 13 visualization panels were created. Some were loosely sequential while others were single panels. Some drawings included several panels that are not sequential, but attempted to show several elements of the same moment.

To follow are four examples of the artwork produced. These were shown to the informants, whose response forms the basis of evaluation later.

Figure 2. Call to adventure. This image intends to express the emotion and experience of the re-designed pre-match press conference. It shows the team manager in action where the focus is more on 'a call to adventure' rather than game facts and statistics. This is a non-sequential single panel.

Figure 3. Call up of players. This image focuses on the experience and emotion generated in a redesign of player call-up. Previously players were contacted through phone or email and the service designer envisaged a scenario where the experience for the player could be heightened by the inclusion of a 'call-up ritual'. This would include a befittingly solemn correspondence, a box and a shirt that would carry the message 'ja vi elsker' ('Yes we love' which is the first line of the Norwegian national anthem) hidden on the inside of the shirt. Here there is no chronological sequence, but 3 panels that show different aspects of the moment at once. It shows the touchpoints of the box and letter opened and players determined look as he understands his destiny.

Figure 4. The Arrival, is chronologically sequential. It shows fans arriving at the national stadium train station, approaching and then arriving at the corner of the stadium. These panels try to express the celebratory and inclusive feel of arriving to watch a national game. It attempts to convey the sense of spectacle and occasion

Figure 5. Music Together. This image visualizes 3 moments happening simultaneously at different

Figure 4. *The Arrival*. Illustration Syver Lauritzen.

places. It tries to depict the sense of ‘solidarity’ when all are listening to the same uplifting music wherever they might be.

Method

Data for this paper was collected through semi-structured interviews from 9 informants:

- 2 informants had been involved with the broader project of football. As designers they were engaged in the branding exercise though not directly involved in the service design part of the project and therefore had no input in the process described here.
- 1 informant was directly involved in the project and represents the football association. Though not directly involved in the development of GEE, they did have input into the forming of some of the images
- 4 informants are practicing service designers.
- 1 informant comes from practice but currently works as a lecturer within the institution where the writer of this paper is associated.
- 1 informant currently works as a lecturer but also as a researcher within service design and practice. Both positioned within the institution where the writer of this paper is associated.

This mix of informants were chosen as they offered:

- An internal design view without being directly involved
- A stakeholder view that could offer insights into how the drawings were used
- An external view from service designers in practice
- An educators view
- A researchers view

Interviews were undertaken face-to-face with one performed via skype. All interviews were conducted by

the author. Most interviews were conducted with a single interviewee, however in one case two persons were interviewed at the same time. 5 interviews took place in English the others in Norwegian.

The interviews were conducted between 18th – 29th January 2016, with the majority taking place at the interviewees’ workplaces.

The interviews for the informants who had no prior knowledge of the process opened with a presentation of the GEE images represented in this paper. They were presented together with the customer journey, with some images of how the service was before and with some standard photographic mock-ups/evidencing. This was done to give context and this also represented how the images had been used during the project when communicating concepts to stakeholders.

Interviews began with an open question that asked the informants their thoughts on the technique through viewing the images, in the context of service design and its current toolkit.

Further questions related to the processes usefulness, usability and originality

When this information was not forthcoming further questions probed what they felt the images tried to express.

All interviews were recorded and transcribed.

These transcriptions were analyzed through a framework based on the theory presented above. This is represented by 2 statements, each with a pair of related research questions that put focus on the GEE model and its relationship to the theory

Figure 5. Music Together. Note: Both the cartoonist (holding 'ja' glass) and this papers author (holding 'elsker' glass) are visualized in the bottom panel. Illustration Syver Lauritzen.

Figure 6. Customer journey also presented to informants. Visualization: Ted Matthews.

1. The graphic novel form has the power to affect the viewer emotionally and to project the experience of the scene represented.
 - a. To what extent does GEE fulfill its intention of expressing and communicating more richly the experience and emotion to viewers?
 - b. To what extent did the images managed to project the brand values and could the projected experience be experienced through experiencing the images?
2. There is a gap in the service design toolkit for more expressive visual techniques for communicating the projected experience and emotion of designed service moments.
 - a. To what extent is GEE an innovation in process? (Given that the need of the project and the perceived lack of an appropriate tool in service design lead to its development)
 - b. How useful does GEE seem for service design practice?

Results

1.a To what extent does GEE fulfill its intention of expressing and communicating more richly the experience and emotion to viewers.

All informants' felt GEE was a good way to show both experience and emotion. This was expressed on general terms. However some went into detail, suggesting that the images managed to project an attitude, with others describing the images as powerful and with the potential to put across meaningful situations. It was uncovered that the images had been used by all the informants involved in the project for communicating the service experience to stakeholders to explain the experience being designed for. This was primarily for decision makers but the images were also used as experiential references for actors involved in delivering the service. For example the team manager was shown Figure 2, Call to adventure, to explain the perceived new experience tonality. These informants described an 'Aha!' moment when the images were viewed,

Figure 7. Stadium mock up also presented to informants. Visualization: Ted Matthews.

suggesting that they revealed something to the viewer. The cartoons however had been used in combination with other service design visualizations, such as customer journeys and mock-ups. They were also used with images from how the service currently is delivered and the contrast with these images they suggested have an additional effect. This was confirmed when informants from outside the project having been presented the drawings in this same way, felt they were more efficacious when used in combination with other contextualizing images and visualizations.

Where it was felt that the drawings communicated both experience and emotion, a couple of informants reported that some of the images themselves didn't hit the mark, either in terms of not conveying the desired feeling exactly of the scene portrayed or that the images had 'gone too far' and were over-the-top. In regards to the last point the informant suggested that this might be down to personal taste, however they did feel that image might be too aggressive pushing the brand values to the limit.

'Call to adventure', however seemed to 'work' for most of the informants and often was referred back to as most successful in conveying the experience. This could be down to the image having a single impact instead of having several panels that have to be 'read' to get the meaning; therefore the experience could be gleaned at once. But referencing back to McCloud it is in stripping down, that the cartoonist delivers the desired intensity and the 'Call to Adventure' is the most stripped down image in terms of number of panels and content.

1.b To what extent did the images managed to project the brand and could the projected experience be experienced through experiencing the images.

A number of informants expressed that they felt the experience from looking at the images (this specifically differing from feeling that the images communicated the desired emotion and experience well). Some of these perceived experiences were mixed with a sense of the brand values expressed through the aesthetics. The brand values were not revealed to the informants who were outside the project, however several suggested they felt the images were macho, edgy, tough and 'angry'. These descriptions match with the brand element 'Ferocity'. Others then suggested that images such as 'The Arrival', instilled feelings of 'patriotism' and in another case 'pride' and 'togetherness'. This matched with the brand elements 'Solidarity' and 'pride'.

The informant working with football felt that the sport had a long association with comic strips making the media ideal for this context. In addition to this point another informant felt that the current popularity of comics made the images more readable for a larger audience.

Insight: This feedback shows that the graphic novel form operationalized for service design through GEE does convey experience and emotion whilst

communicating the brand. For some viewing the images did give them an experience of the experience. The single image appears to be the most successful in conveying these elements but to what extent this is due to its style and execution rather than its non-chronological nature isn't known.

2.a To what extent is GEE an innovation in process?

Using OECD's definition we understand innovation in process to mean:

'The implementation of a new or significantly improved production or delivery method. This includes significant changes in techniques, equipment and/or software.'

Most of the informants had seen the use of cartoons as part of the service design process. This has been mainly observed in the simple communication of the service flow and interaction sometimes in customer journeys, sometimes in storyboards. These cartoons were often little more than stick figures describing interactions. Cartoons are also used by service designers as a way to facilitate conversation with clients. These images then often remain in the process after this point as the customer gets to know them. None of the informants had seen cartoons used in this particular way or so 'expressive'. One informant felt that GEE represented an 'upgraded component' of the service design toolkit, where service design outsourced elements of the process to better skilled individuals. Others expressed that the technique had an advantage over media that convey the experience over time, like film or storyboarding, as it could communicate things happening simultaneously. It therefore allowed the viewer to take great leaps of context, that through a single panel it was possible to get the feel, meaning and experience of a key moment or meaningful situation. For a number of informants the image that used a single panel was the greatest departure from what they had seen before. Where a single composition through the expressive construction of the graphic artist was able to put across 'big ideas' and that through the cartoon form could take away elements that could distract the viewer from the 'meaning' of the designed moment.

2.b How useful does GEE seem for service design practice?

Beyond many of the respondents expressing loosely that they could imagine using the technique in their work others expanded on this theme. The informant who worked within the football association explained how the images took, the at times complex and near academic concepts and made them accessible for others. That they made less 'dangerous' and approachable. This informant went on to say they would need more as part of the on going work. Some expressed that getting the feeling and focus right using photos and mock ups would be very difficult and that such techniques can sometime feel fake and inauthentic. For these informants GEE as executed in this project gave focus to the elements that mattered, to the meaning, to the experience and emotion as you

are allowed yourself to fill in the blanks.

Several informants said that they would start using the technique in their own work and that others who had seen the work were looking to source cartoonists who could carry out similar assignments.

Some informants were concerned that the technique might represent increased costs that would be difficult to justify to clients. This view is tempered however by one informant who felt the technique could be used instead of and more effectively than expensive mock-ups.

Insight: As GEE does represent an innovation in process for service design it shows that there is a gap in the field for such a technique. The level of this innovation is not fully known and where it might not be revolutionary it appears to offer a fine tuning of existing techniques for generating experience samples. Adoption shows perceived usefulness. GEE also offers a real alternative to other tools such as the mockup for conveying experience and has an advantage over time base media, where the graphic novel can show simultaneous events in different contexts.

Discussion and further work

In general this data reveals a level of agreement between those who experienced GEE in use and those who were presented the outcomes, relating to the usefulness of the technique, its ability to communicate experience and emotion, its originality and as a useful tool in combination with others.

For a further insight it would be useful to collect data from those who received the presentation within the football association so getting a sense of how the images made the intended audience feel, rather than relying on designers who through their profession might have heightened susceptibility to 'feel' the projected experience.

Those outside the project were presented the drawings in the same way they were used in the project to replicate how they were used in practice. It would be interesting in further research to use two groups, one that viewed the drawings in context and the other that just viewed the images alone. This would help conclude if the drawings really do need the other tools to support their understanding.

Much of the feedback suggested that the single panel illustration worked best in conveying the 'feel', 'meaning', 'tone', 'emotion', 'big story' of the service moment. As has been mentioned this could be down to being able to understand the meaning and experience in a single panel. But as it was raised by one informant that their response to the actual execution of the image affected their evaluation, it could be the case with the single panel that this one just happened to be 'well drawn' for purpose. Here more research should be done where different styles and single or a series of panels could communicate the same service moment. With a test group this could give more insight into what works best.

Several of the designers picked up on the brand values experienced through the images. In addition it was suggested that the graphic novel style lends itself to football due to a tradition of cartoons and soccer in children's comics, i.e. Roy of the Rovers. Therefore further work is currently underway to try the technique in the service context of banking and whilst trying to reflect the brands values.

Cost was raised as an issue and the author can confirm that some images took up to eight hours to produce. However dependent on the client, type service and the potential of saving on producing other types of mock-ups the cost might be justifiable given that the technique shows advantage over other forms of experience communication.

Reflecting on the collaboration with the cartoonist, it was key to use enough time at the start to go through as much of the context as possible so they could really understand what the project was about. Also it became clear that trusting in the cartoonists own vision and skill lead to unexpected, yet superior solutions than the service designer could have envisaged. These aleatory responses in turn informed the further development of the final service design solution.

This study suggests originality and a level of innovation for GEE as a new tool within the context of Service Design. One informant used the word 'Upgrade' to describe the technique, but this was when comparing it to storyboarding. However the image that moved furthest away from sequential communication seemed to have the greatest impact and seen as the greatest innovation in conveying many elements of the service moment in a new way. The further tests mentioned above should uncover the level of 'significant change' that OECD alludes to.

Conclusion

Introducing tools of this nature has implication for the way that service design now develops over the next few years. This study shows that there are gaps in the current service design toolkit and there is much potential for the field to find more expressive ways to deliver an experience sample to others.

Graphic Experiential Evidencing does offer an expansion of the current visualization methods to detail the dramaturgy of the experience and desired emotional response for designed service moments. How radical an expansion is still not known.

In combination with existing service design visualization techniques, GEE communicates well the desired experience to audiences of stakeholders. Referencing to Suri, the technique does indeed create a common vision and richer representation, making the experience more tangible during the design process itself.

GEE also has great potential as a replacement or supplement to service scripts, where actors get to 'feel' their role rather than be told it.

More research needs to be undertaken to understand

further how the process might be developed and improved for repeatable, on target results across different kinds of services and in different brand styles. This research might show to what extent an experience might be experienced through this form of visual media.

It is hoped that this paper could encourage further research on how service design might expand its toolkit to encourage the design of increasingly experiential service offerings.

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Happiness-related qualities of mobile apps for physical activity

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Abstract Many studies concentrate on the use of persuasive technology to encourage people for active lifestyles, yet it is a design challenge to create intrinsic motivation for users to increase or maintain healthy behaviour. Building upon the relationship between happiness and staying active, this paper presents design qualities perceived as a source of happiness. The study empirically examines data gathered from semi-structured, in-depth interviews of 20 people between the ages of 20 and 30. It applies content analysis method to analyze product qualities associated with happiness in relation to users' short-term experiences with smart mobile applications. Benefiting from the theory of wellness, the paper explores the qualities of mobile physical activity apps and proposes possibilities for happiness.

Keywords *Happiness, Mobile application, Subjective well-being, Physical activity*

Introduction

Inactivity negatively affects human health and well-being (Warburton et al., 2006). The widespread prevalence of a sedentary lifestyle increases attention towards developing interventions for encouraging physical activity (Biddle et al., 2004). Smart mobile phones appear as efficient tools to intervene physical inactivity since they enable ubiquitous access to people (Fanning, Mullen & McAuley, 2012).

The major body of research and product development for physical activity carries the intention to increase one's level of activity via ubiquitous and mobile technology. The interventions adopt a *persuasive technology* framework (Fogg, 2002; Chatterjee & Price, 2009; Lehto & Oinas-Kukkonen, 2011). Despite such mobile persuasive strategies, studies show that people still encounter difficulties in maintaining their motivation for physical activity and there appear ethical concerns of making someone to do something (Arteaga et al., 2009; Dorrestijn & Paul-Verbeek, 2013; Fogg, 2009; Olofsson, 2010). Some studies document the importance of the role of positive feelings in users' motivation for physical activity (Fujuki et al., 2008; Arteaga, 2009), however, the literature lacks a perspective that would address the inner needs as a source of physical activity. Knowing that happier people are more active and motivated to set and achieve goals, understanding the possibilities associated with people's happiness become fundamental (Schulz, 1985; Ryan & Deci, 2000; Veenhoven, 2008). For this purpose, applying the positive psychology approach to design seems to be a relevant starting point (Schot et al., 2009; Desmet & Hassenzahl, 2012; Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013).

Happiness is a challenging concept and approached differently by various researchers (Diener et al., 1984, 2000; Ryff, 1989; Ryan & Deci, 2000; Csikszentmihalyi & Hunter, 2003; Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2005;

Seligman, 2008; Seligman, 2011). Although a global definition of happiness has not been agreed upon, affect and cognition are commonly regarded as two main dimensions of it. Taking a hybrid view of these, Seligman (2011) describes well-being in terms of positive emotions, engagement, relationship, sense of meaning, and achievement (PERMA); respectively interpreted as feeling good about one's self, living in flow, connecting with others, and having a sense of meaning and goal accomplishment.

Happiness-related qualities of mobile applications

Our empirical study explored properties of mobile phone apps that carry possibilities to address needs regarding happiness. In our results section, we present design dimensions that may contribute to happiness.

Selection of mobile applications

For this study, we selected four free iPhone apps based on probability and disproportionate sampling. Among 16,499 health and exercise apps in the iTunes store Turkey, we examined 375 most popular applications of which 142 focused on physical activity. We eliminated 56 non-free of those apps to ensure the chosen apps would be accessible to all users. The next cut was based on app scores provided by previous users; those that scored below 3.5 over 5.0 were eliminated on account of low perceived credibility. Next, considering an app's possibilities for evoking happiness, from among different categorization methods for physical activity apps (Ahtinen et al., 2008; West et al., 2012; Kranz et al., 2012), we chose Ahtinen et al.'s (2008) because it concentrates on motivation and classifies the apps into four groups: personal trainer, logger, playful applications and games, and social applications. Finally, after categorizing our remaining apps, we ranked them based on their public ratings, and chose for our study the leading app in each category: Nike Training Club (personal trainer), Sports

Nike Training Club (personal trainer app) provides users with a list of workouts based on their goals and fitness levels by showing videos by actual personal trainers. It gives rewards and allows sharing info with friends. Users can listen to music and receive audio feedback during their workouts.

Sports Tracker (logger app) keeps track of an outdoor workout on the map by using GPS, logs it automatically to system, and monitors progress of workouts.

Fit for Rhythm (playful app) counts the number of repetitions of the demonstrated exercise the user performs, accompanied by a virtual coach. The user must have the iPhone in hand for this app to work.

Fitocracy (social app) provides a platform on which to log workouts manually and track, share and learn new exercises while receiving support from the community of app users.

Figure 1. Snapshots of apps.

Tracker (logger), Fit for Rhythm (playful), and Fitocracy (social) (Figure 1).

Participants

In order to fairly represent people with different interests in and desire for physical activity, we selected participants via non-probability quota sampling by looking at their level of physical activity through a stages of change (SoC) scale (Marcus & Simkin, 1993). The scale determines people's level of activity by acquiring knowledge about their exercise routines. We selected our sample group from among people in every stage excluding Stage 1 (state of physical inactivity with a lack of intent to be physically active in the next six months).

The second criteria for participant selection was being owner of an iPhone and having enough knowledge of English to use applications well. We chose young adults because of the growing importance of sedentary habits among young people associated with health problems in later life (Owen et al., 2014) and familiarity with mobile apps. Participation was voluntary and participants selected applications they

had never used.

The sample contained 11 female and 9 male undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral students between the ages of 20 and 30, with a mean value of 24.2. Among the 20 participants, P10 and P14 stopped using the applications after their second experience (of the required three), respectively due to an unrelated health problem and disengagement with the application because some exercises were unavailable for logging.

Study methods

Our empirical study consisted of three phases: (i) a semi-structured entry interview to introduce the apps and understand users' perceptions about apps, (ii) a diary for users to record their three experiences over one week in real time, and (iii) a semi-structured exit interview to probe product qualities associated with happiness (Table 2).

Because each person's level of happiness is different (Diener, 2000), before the first interview we asked participants to complete a scale of positive and

Table 1. Information on Participants and Application Preferences.

App	Nike Training Club							Fit for Rhythm							Sports Tracker			Fitocracy		
Participant	P1	P3	P7	P10	P11	P18	P19	P4	P5	P6	P9	P13	P16	P20	P2	P12	P17	P8	P14	P15
SoC	S5	S2	S4	S3	S5	S4	S5	S2	S2	S4	S2	S2	S3	S4	S3	S3	S3	S4	S5	S5
Sex	F	F	F	M	F	M	M	F	F	M	M	F	F	M	F	F	F	M	M	M
Age	30	22	23	27	29	20	22	21	25	23	23	27	24	25	26	22	24	23	24	24
Affect Balance	15	-4	-12	1	4	16	11	6	11	13	-4	13	10	19	11	10	3	3	18	13

negative experiences (SPANE) developed by Diener et al. (2009) so we could determine their affect balance. The aim of this scale is to understand a participant's positive and negative experiences (affect balance level) over the preceding month and, in our case, to determine whether past negative experiences may affect his/her experience with the app or not. Only three participants (P3, P7, P9) had negative scores for SPANE, and the exit interview determined that these participants could more easily disengage with the applications, a finding that needs further analysis.

After determining the affect balances, participants were shown the four apps and their perceptions about each app was analyzed. The apps were introduced by showing a card that consisted of the name, version number, five screen shots of the app, and a short description of the key features. Then, participants were asked to select one of the apps based on his/her usage aims.

In the second phase, participants were expected to use one of the applications three times over approximately one week and take notes right after each session, documenting what (would) made them happy during the experience. Usage duration was determined by referencing similar studies (Romero et al., 2010), which used a one-week diary method with the day-reconstruction technique to determine people's likes in their daily routines. After each session, to prevent memory bias in recalling their emotions later, participants were asked to send us their notes and to fill in a physical activity enjoyment questionnaire (PACES) (Marcus et al., 1993), a seven-point semantic-differential scale that evaluates enjoyment levels. The scale was to aid in understanding users' level of enjoyment at the moment they performed an activity with the app.

In the third phase, that is, at the end of the one-week period, participants were asked to recount their

experiences so we could explore possibilities related to happiness and physical activity when using mobile apps.

Data analysis

We performed content analysis (Krippendorff, 2004) on the in-depth interviews, concentrating on product properties associated with happiness. Using a coding technique with predefined codes from the literature (Saldana, 2009), we conceptualized the patterns observed in the data into a model representing the characteristics of mobile physical activity applications that evoke happiness. An example of coding is given in Table 3.

Design qualities of mobile physical activity applications that evoke happiness

In this section, we explain design qualities related to the possibilities they hold for increasing happiness. Regarding the fact that happiness is a complex and multidimensional concept with subjective characteristics, we bring the approaches of wellness and wellbeing together to express a holistic viewpoint. Our model shown in Figure 2 represents seven domains of wellness by Roscoe (2009) (outer circle), relevant dimensions of wellbeing theory by Seligman (2011) (middlemost circle), and the design qualities in mobile apps obtained by the empirical study (inner circle). Since these qualities are likely to affect the experienced wellness type, the affected qualities of well-being vary. Each design quality is explained in the follows.

Emotional wellness

According to Renger et al. (2000) emotional wellness considers a person's degree of anxiety, depression, well-being, self-control, and optimism. Life satisfaction, interest, and enjoyment are also aspects of emotional wellness.

Table 2. Study Phases.

Phases	Method	Tool	Aim
First	First semi-structured in-depth interview	SPANE	Evaluating affect balance of participants Selection of app
Second	3 usages (~1 week)	Diary Method PACES	Keeping record of experiences in time. Measuring enjoyment in time.
Third	Second semi-structured in-depth interview, conducted at the end of three usages.		Understanding app qualities that evoked positive emotions; in what ways the app created life satisfaction; in what ways the app shifted feelings into a positive/negative state.

Table 3. Coding Example.

Transcription	Wellness Type	Causal	Affected	Talking About
"The reason it made me feel positive is because when I was studying, my mind was full of thoughts, and exercising with [this] simple app worked in freeing my mind and created positivity."	Emotional	Simplicity	Flow	Experiencing flow during a simple activity with the app

Figure 2. Model of Design Qualities.

From a well-being perspective, we observed that the apps contained the possibility of enhancing positive emotions, engagement, and life satisfaction. Positive emotions are related to emotional wellness on basis of the availability of positive emotions rather than negative ones. Engagement is associated with enjoyment of life (Csikszentmihalyi and Hunter, 2003), and this study reveals that if users enjoy the activity performed with the app, it increases pleasurable moments in their lives and encourages them to perform the activity again. Life satisfaction corresponds to a sense of goal accomplishment. As many people view physical activity as a goal to achieve, working towards this also enhances emotional wellness.

The results of our empirical study show that flow, accomplishment, and personalizing physical activity apps enhance emotional wellness. The following sections explain these qualities with respect to design dimensions.

Flow

Participants' comments regarding positive emotions associated with the apps express the connection of happiness with the flow that can occur during physical activity. A product that provides users a sense of full concentration during physical activity may contribute to the process of freeing the mind and creating at least short-term happiness.

P9: "The reason it made me feel positive is because when I was studying, my mind was full of thoughts, and exercising with [this] simple app worked in freeing my mind and created positivity."

Simplicity of the interface, trustworthiness of the application, and coaching given while the exercise is being performed (what we also call simultaneous coaching) are all deemed important to experience flow during physical activity performed with an app.

Simplicity

Simplicity of the interface is necessary because an app must be easy to comprehend in order to establish and maintain focus.

P2: "If it is aiming to encourage physical activity, it should definitely be easy to use. I should log whatever I want with ease and speed or I should control the data in an easier way."

Trustworthiness

To engage users in the activity performed, trustworthiness is important. Doubting the accuracy of the information provided by the app breaks concentration, which negatively affects flow.

P6: "There was a punching part of the application. Sometimes, I see it is not counting when I punch and sometimes I see that it has counted although I have not punched. ...In that sense I felt unhappy, [wondering] why it is not working correctly."

Simultaneity

The simultaneity of the movement visuals/videos shown together with the activity affects users in terms of flow. Instead of concentrating on the activity, by having users try to understand the move, the applications cannot guide them to an enjoyable experience. Therefore, users seek for simultaneity.

P7: *"Watching while performing is better, of course. It is not a TV, but while performing, you must be watching how it is performed at the same time.... You are stopping at each move, thinking, 'How I was doing that?' or checking the app if you are confused.... To make it easier, you should be able to watch how the coach is doing it, while the timer is on."*

Achievement

Another dimension that affects emotional wellness is a sense of achievement. Selecting an activity, meeting its challenges, setting goals, self-monitoring, and seeing results contributes to a feeling of accomplishment, which feeds self-efficacy. Achievement, as a result of goal accomplishment has a long-lasting positive effect on eudemonic well-being. Achievement is also associated with higher exercise duration, performance, and motivation.

Duration

Users, especially those not habitually physically active, want shorter durations with motivating feedback when performing physical activity.

P16: *"Even in that moment, you feel the sense of accomplishment. Ok, you have finished these five; you have completed the last three and so on."*

Performance

An efficient performance that results in observable outcomes, for example, the feeling of exertion, experienced in shorter duration increases a sense of achievement.

P1: *"... There is a thing called the sense of accomplishment. If I accomplish [something], I should accomplish it efficiently and on time. And I should accomplish it ideally in terms of performance."*

Motivation

Our data analysis shows that a user's level of motivation affects his or her sense of achievement. A higher level of motivation enhances emotional wellness with respect to experiencing awareness for physical activity, challenge, self-monitoring, feedback, and goal setting.

Appropriate goal-setting, optimal level of challenge, and reachability of goals are necessary to increase motivation and hence happiness.

P8: *"What makes me happy is ... gaining points as you perform physical activity, passing levels and communication with others."*

Gaining awareness for physical activity is found to be a motivating aspect. Especially for users in the lower SoCs, the apps can be a tool for increasing awareness of the activities they perform, because the apps can change users' perceptions about activity as being only vigorous exercise.

P12: *"Normally, I walk in my daily life, but it is not like doing sports. Well, I sometimes walk to perform physical activity and sometimes to free my mind, but I did not feel as if I was doing sports previously, not*

like people who go to a sports center or swimming. But when I used this application I felt like I was doing sports."

Applications enable feedback mostly via written information or a type of summary such as a graph. According to our results, users want a dialogue of support, and particularly praise and suggestions for improvement. From a design perspective, the comprehension and relevance of feedback to a user is extremely important. Besides self-monitoring is a strong motivator because it may recall past achievements. Therefore, it contributes to self-improvement and motivation.

Personalization

The individualistic nature of physical activity requires personalization of the app if it aims to suggest an activity to a user, and users frequently mentioned the need for personalized interaction. Most of the apps provide only standardized content; from a design perspective, a user could incorporate personal information, thus allowing the app to evaluate the user's experience and suggest moves and workouts based on that data. The application, in this respect, would be expected to be smart and like an interactive personal coach.

P1: *"I wish it gave smart suggestions. I mean, I pause, for example. The application is most probably seeing that I paused, I paused for a long time, or I stopped. I wish it asked if the exercise was difficult, what happened, and make suggestions for the next time accordingly: 'If you were not able to do that, then try this.' You are doing it on your own, otherwise."*

Because applications do not allow personalization to a great extent, users experienced issues with trustworthiness, causing displeasure. They also commented on the need to increase interaction through an interface that keeps personal data and suggests personalized activities fitting their abilities and interests.

Social wellness

One of the dimensions of Renger et al.'s (2000) definition of social wellness is the interaction of an individual with other people. In terms of the theory of well-being, relationships and social support are considered necessary for positive connections with others (Seligman, 2011). Therefore, being connected to others in a secure way is associated with social wellness.

Connectedness

Some users enjoyed the social facilitation and competition aspects of the apps because they made the activity fun. In terms of social learning and social facilitation, using the app with others, especially friends, was enjoyable.

P8: *"In fact, using it with a few more friends would make it more enjoyable."*

However, some people feel that exercise is more of a personal activity, and for them, social comparison

evoked negative feelings.

P3: "I do not know why, but I do not believe it is a necessity to do sports and share it with others. You do it alone then stop exercising. I do not think it is a thing to be shared with others."

Applications have the capability to connect to social media and share information. Among the participants preferring to perform physical activity alone, we observed that the possibility of sharing through social media causes trust issues around the application; users expect such access to be user-managed.

P2: "Wondering if it would be connected to the Internet or social media disturbed me. The "Connect to Facebook" inscription could be presented in the settings or it could be in a less-central location on the screen. Instead, it is in the middle of the screen, which I might press by accident.... I do not want to connect, enter the site, and open an account.... I find knowing that I control it makes me feel relaxed."

Assistive interaction

Another social aspect is the relationship between users and apps. Apps appear to make it easier for users to exercise, through periodic reminders, keeping records, and providing a suggestion dialogue. Therefore, apps establish a type of social relationship with user.

P7: "The application reminds that you should do this now and what you are doing is good. The phone reminder and the application are different things in my opinion. When the phone reminds you it feels like the phone belongs to you. But the application is not like it belongs to you; it is like you have to do what it says. You feel you are being monitored by the coaches; it feels like you have to do it. You can turn off the alarm of the phone but when it comes from the application, it is like, yes, the coach is waiting for me. And you are getting up and going."

Because there is a social relationship between the user and the app, the most desirable characteristic of the latter in that regard is a friendly, human persona who utters non-commanding statements. Personification, in that sense, is believed to positively affect social wellness.

P10: "That robotic voice was the most irritating, disturbing thing. In the other application that I used to use, you are exercising... while the coach is visible and using a normal human voice. But here it shows you the video, closes it and has that robotic voice. It should be a human, a human voice. It would be more engaging."

Physical wellness

Adams et al. (1997) define the concept of physical wellness as the perception and evaluation of physical fitness, and Durlak (2000) adds physical competencies and behaviours (habits and level of activity) to this definition. Based on these viewpoints, for our study we consider physical wellness as the perception of the physical state at the moment physical activity is

performed with the app, and the feeling of strength that emerges as a result of the exercise.

Physical exertion

A user's comfort level will determine whether the user will be bored with the level of difficulty of the exercise or will enjoy the exercise. If there is enjoyment, there will be a feeling of flow. If the moves are too challenging or too simple, users are likely to get bored and give up the physical activity and the app.

P1: "It does not give breaks. I am getting tired and out of breath, sweating in a meaningless way... My knees were like aching. Finally, I gave up at the twelfth minute. I got bored. For example, it is asking to do a single led for two minutes. How can I do it for two minutes?... The third move was simpler. It gave breaks but it did not contribute anything. I did not feel any stretch. As I am already doing it when I am at home, I feel bored."

Users' perceptions of their physical fitness and the app's trustworthiness were negatively affected if the moves were too challenging, not challenging enough, and/or not personalized. So as not to cause over- or under-exertion, users perceive personalization as important.

Personalization

To enhance physical wellness through apps, personalized interaction is crucial. Users seek personalization to be able to make changes to the list of suggested workouts. Even if the content is tailored to the needs of a user group, individual users can experience various difficulties or trust issues.

P10: "The app asked me what do I want to do in general and I exercised according to that. On the other hand, it did not suggest anything by taking information on height, weight, personal characteristics... etc. Therefore, within the exercises it sets, there are also moves that I cannot do.... For example, while doing crunches... it could say do a half crunch since a full crunch may injure you because you have a problem with your weight.... But it shows a standard version to everybody."

Another reason for personalization is users' doubts about whether the moves suggested by the app are safe. These doubts can affect the app's level of trustworthiness and in turn, flow.

P11: "When I do not know whether I do the move correctly or not, I may also get injured. I feel unsure about that."

Achievement

Users are likely to feel a sense of accomplishment when they experience optimal physical exertion in terms of the moves, level of difficulty, and duration.

P6: "I continue to feel happier and invigorated as I continue using the application. Because the exercise is accomplished in a short time, I feel happy. I can easily do and accomplish the exercises, therefore I feel happy. It satisfies me."

Spiritual wellness

Adams et al. (2000) define spiritual wellness as having a sense of meaning and purpose in life, and having a connection to the self, the environment and a higher power. Seligman's (2011) well-being theory, in line with that, defines meaning and purpose as "feeling of belonging and serving something larger than the self."

Spiritual wellness can be enhanced by establishing a sense of belonging and relatedness. Setting a goal with lofty manners for physical activity can both increase one's sense of accomplishment and being related to an event or activity while feeding spirituality. Combined with lofty goals, being connected to others in a common purpose may thus increase spiritual wellness.

P4: "In order to attain a feeling of satisfaction, the app should be broader. It is like a competition. Or it should serve the purpose of a lofty aim. It is not that lofty. I did it, took part for my own enjoyment. I enjoyed it but that is all. If I do physical activity, I want to make a show of it or do it for a charity. However, I only did it for myself."

Intellectual wellness

Renger et al. (2000) define intellectual wellness as an "individual's perception, one's orientation and achievement toward personal growth". Consequently, being knowledgeable about one's physical activity to achieve a goal can improve intellectual wellness.

Novelty

Novelty of information contributes to personal growth. Therefore, users feel positive about learning new information and are in search of information that surprises them. Novel can mean different things depending on the app. Playful applications are expected to provide novel content through which users can experience different activities each time they use the app. In coaching apps, suggesting new activities/moves is important, and in tracking apps, novelty is associated with new self-monitoring data. Novelty in social apps stems from new information contributed by other users.

P15: "First of all, you can learn new information with this application. You can discover things you didn't know. It is valid for all areas of the life. If it teaches you something you do not know, then I feel it is good."

Relation to real life

Receiving novel information is more effective in enhancing intellectual wellness when the user can integrate the information into everyday life. Providing information or tips for the real world instead of giving estimations and calculations on activity leads to positive emotions and motivation. Real-life information can be in the form of seeking real friends performing physical activity, using the application for social facilitation, receiving content fed by real people's opinions, seeing real people coaching them through the app, or most interestingly, gaining rewards that establish a sense of reality in the admittedly artificial world of the app.

P13: "The app could provide references that are more realistic. For example, "The sportsmen of this kind do this with that number of repetitions, so let's begin with that many repetitions. By giving information related to real life, for example, if there are these yoga moves, then giving information about it (the moves are those, they work for those, they make these muscles work) would be more convincing."

Environmental wellness

Roscoe (2009) specifies the concept of environmental wellness as a balance of interacting with the environment by contributing to its welfare and being aware of one's effects on nature. Encouraging outdoor physical activity via an app can increase time spent in nature.

P12: "Going to a sports center seems like a mandatory task. On the other hand, going out for a walk is for relaxation and fresh air. First of all, I dislike sport center[s] and being indoors. There are many people around doing exercise. It may help psychologically but I see it as a task.... Being outdoors is more natural. Besides, the weather is nicer outdoors. Therefore, I prefer exercising in the outdoors."

Occupational wellness

Hettler (1980) defines occupational wellness as satisfaction felt through work. Crose et al. (1992), however, emphasize a balance between work and leisure. From participants' comments, a busy schedule at work/school can prevent physical activity.

P15: "I had been feeling very bad about not performing sports. I had exams and a busy schedule at work. Therefore, I did not have any time for physical activity."

The duration of an activity is an important factor in exercise, and even short periods of physical activity have the potential to evoke happiness and enhance occupational wellness by contributing to goal accomplishment and by improving the balance between work and leisure.

P16: "I thought that I did something for myself during the day. Above all, I thought of myself as a person who spends time efficiently; I am waking up in the morning, doing exercise and going to work. It became something that made me happy with myself."

Discussion

The preceding discussion is summarized in Figure 3. The figure describes apps' design qualities with respect to its possibilities for evoking happiness, and gives related design implications.

Conclusion

Our research has implications for designers and developers who aim to design mobile apps for physical activity with a lens of happiness. The work here frames the pool of possibilities by combining the theory of wellness, wellbeing and the outcomes of the empirical study. The contribution of this study has been to introduce the directions in which physical activity would be associated with happiness

DESIGN QUALITIES

DESIGN IMPLICATIONS

<p>Emotional</p> <p>flow simplicity trustworthiness simultaneity</p> <p>achievement duration performance motivation</p> <p>personalization</p>	<p>A product contributing to flow stimulates concentration and feeling released from the concerns of interaction. A product facilitates autonomy if it comprises a comprehensible, simple interface, trustworthy interaction that does not cause confusion, and simultaneous guidance where the user feels in control of the situation. Personalized interaction helps to maintain user autonomy and leverages a sense of uniqueness. Achieving goals feeds self-efficacy.</p>
<p>Physical</p> <p>physical exertion personalization</p> <p>achievement</p>	<p>Personalized workouts contribute to satisfaction and autonomy and help to mitigate concerns around security. Experiencing a sense of achievement by accomplishing exercise tasks through optimal exercison increases competency.</p>
<p>Intellectual</p> <p>novelty reality</p>	<p>Information's novelty and its relation to real life feeds personal growth and gives sense of competency.</p>
<p>Occupational</p> <p>duration</p>	<p>Work usually occupies the majority of working time in one's day, but the possibility of exercising with mobile apps may encourage people to take better care of self by fitting in exercise, and thus increase happiness through better balance of work and leisure time.</p>
<p>Spiritual</p> <p>goal loftiness</p>	<p>Through physical activity, a feeling of satisfaction by serving something larger than self may be enhanced by establishing a sense of belongingness and relatedness.</p>
<p>Social</p> <p>connectedness assistive interaction</p>	<p>Because preferences for connection to other people differ depending on users' SoCs and affect balances, designing for user control over connection and socialization levels is necessary. The interaction between the user and the app itself is also an important design consideration, given the importance users placed on human-like app characteristics.</p>
<p>Environmental</p> <p>balance</p>	<p>Encouraging physical activity through mobile apps can increase a user's positive interaction with nature.</p>

Figure 3. Summary of Design Qualities and Implications for Design.

enhancing design qualities. These may take many forms, ranging from emotional to spiritual wellness. Further research could examine specific user groups with a certain level of activity, and analyze the implications of using the apps in the long term.

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How does car seat appearance influence perceived comfort

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Abstract Automotive seat comfort has become a major aspect in differentiation and customisation amongst competitors in a highly saturated automotive market. Unlike discomfort, the concept of comfort is regarded a highly subjective and multi-faceted phenomenon. This paper describes an experimental study to explore the differences in the perception of comfort brought about by the mere manipulation of the visual appearance in otherwise two identical automotive seats. In particular it will investigate the hypothesised underlying mechanisms related to the concepts of product personality and affective responses, thereby proposing a theoretical model. In addition, as hypothesised the results showed significant gender effect where by female participants were found to be considerably more sensitive to the impact of visual appearance on comfort. The results are discussed in the context of potential underlying mechanisms relating visual appearance to aesthetics, emotion, and product personality and user image. Suggestions for future studies are provided with regards to visual design parameters and their effect on the perception of automotive seat comfort.

Keywords *Automotive seat, Comfort experience, Product appearance, Product personality, Self-congruence*

Introduction

The car seat is the largest significant point of interaction (Zenk et al., 2008), which plays an important role in the overall impression and appeal of a vehicle (Pinkelman, 2006). In terms of automobile seat comfort and design, the consumer's expectations are getting higher and more demanding (Kolich & Taboun, 2004; Millet & Pignède, 2001; Zenk, Mergl, Hartung, Sabbah, & Bubb, 2006). As successful seats mean returning consumers (Youngs, 2012), most research has focussed on the elimination of discomfort by ergonomic design of the seat (Zenk et al., 2006). The aim of the research presented here, however, is to focus on comfort instead for reasons that will be explored in more detail below. Discomfort is strongly related to posture and has been attributed to factors such as vibration, pressure distribution, and thermal conditions (Vink, 2005). Over time, these factors can lead to discomfort symptoms such as pain and fatigue (see Table 1) (Helander & Zhang, 1997; Millet & Pignède, 2001). Based on empirical evidence, Helander (2003) argued that users of chairs had a better understanding and agreement of discomfort factors compared to comfort factors. Following these findings, he suggested that comfort had to be defined independently of discomfort and measured on a different scale rather than treating "Comfort" and "Discomfort" as bipolar end-points of a scale (Helander, 2003). Vink (2005) has also indicated that absence of discomfort does not necessarily mean direct sensation of comfort and further argued that in order to notice comfort, more should be experienced. Zhang, Helander, & Drury (1996) identified that, "Comfort" related to aesthetics, a sense of relaxation and well-being (see Table 1).

Helander (2003) further argued that, these "comfort" factors; (also synonymously defined as "chair user satisfaction" factors), produced significant differences between chairs for users. Indicating analogies with Maslow's theory of job satisfaction and seat comfort, Helander (2003) suggested that these "satisfaction factors" regarding the users had clearer design implications. In a similar understanding, Quality Function Deployment (QFD) methods are well established in defining satisfying attributes in products (Franceschini, 2001). Specifically in this context, the Kano's model suggests that attributes which "attract" and "delight" the customer lead to a higher level of satisfaction and contribute to differentiation of a particular product. In the automotive context, the styling; look and feel of automotive seats are regarded as differentiating attributes (Kolich, 2008). These attributes of seats have been reported to have a significant effect on driver's seat comfort in surveys such as the JD power and associates APEAL (Pinkelman, 2006). Supportive of these arguments, Mergl, Furlinger, & Bubb, (2008) empirically found that within automotive seats that

Table 1. Factors associated with Comfort & Discomfort during sitting.

Discomfort	Comfort
Fatigue	Impression (Luxury, plush etc.)
Pain/Biomechanics	Safety
Posture	Relief/ Energy
Stiffness/Strains	Well-Being
Heavy legs/Circulation	Relaxation

Source: (P. Vink, 2005; Vink, P., Brauer, Klaus., 2011; Zhang et al., 1996)

Figure 1. Experimental seats employed: drape concealed seat (left), the Black seat (middle) and Grey seat (right).

provide optimal support in an experiment, the effect size of the visual effect was larger than the physically distinguishable differences. In other words, visual appearance had a bigger effect on the perception of comfort than physical changes to the design. Furthermore, previous studies into automotive seat evaluations displayed that, females tended to be more sensitive to the visual appearance of seats than males, although it was not clear whether this also affected the perception of comfort as this was not assessed (Zenk et al., 2008). Moss (2009) stated that visual and tactile information affect emotional outcome and preference in product experience. Literature on product design affords to indicate that gender affects people's choices and influence the experience with products which may influence comfort feelings (Kalviainen, 2002).

This paper investigates the effects of the appearance on seated comfort. In line with findings by Mergl et al. (2008), we previously have demonstrated that changes in the visual appearance of otherwise identical seats can have a significant effect on the perception of comfort (Erol, Diels, Shippen, Richards, & Johnson (2014). Here we try to better understand the underlying mechanisms by considering a range of seating comfort descriptors previously identified to be related to seating comfort in both automotive and non-automotive environments (Helander & Zhang, 1997; Sohlman & Staaf, 2006). The elicited emotional effects of visual design on seat comfort are of interest. We hypothesise that emotional response associated with an automotive seat in terms of comfort encompasses medium levels of pleasantness and slight arousal (Kamp, 2012; Zenk et al., 2008; Knoll, 2006). In return we also propose that the positive emotional effect will affect the perception of comfort, leading to higher overall comfort ratings (Knoll, 2006). We also hypothesise that, in terms of the response to the seat appearance, gender differences will have an effect on the overall comfort and relevant descriptors ratings (Kalviainen, 2002).

Self-congruity theory, suggests that consumers compare their self-concept with the product-user image of a product (Sirgy, 1982). As an extension of this theory Govers (2004), proposed that products

conveying a personality similar to that of the individual (i.e. high level of product personality congruence) tend to be evaluated more favourable (Govers & Schoormans, 2005; Govers, 2004; Sirgy & Johar, 1999). We subsequently also hypothesize that the "product evaluation", is affected by product personality congruence and user-image congruence (Govers, 2004). Product evaluation has been based on items such as a product being beautiful, a product being perceived as a good, being attractive and on willingness to have the particular product (Govers & Schoormans, 2005). We therefore hypothesise in similar perspective that product-personality congruence and user image congruence have a positive effect on the "product evaluation" as provided by findings of Govers & Schoormans (2005). In return we propose that positive self-congruence may have a positive influence on emotional response where the perception of overall comfort of seats may be affected.

Method

Participants

A total of 18 participants (9 male, 9 female) took part in the study, with a mean age of 33.8 years (min=22, max=52, SD= 9.6). At least 3 years driving experience was required for participation. The mean number of years participants held a valid driving licence was 12.3 (SD=10.7).

Seats

The seats used in this study were the front driver and passenger seat of a mid-segment Sedan (Ford Mondeo Mk3). The seats were fitted with two visually different commercially available seat covers: the "Streetwise accessories" (henceforth referred to as the "Black seat") and "Ultimate speed" (henceforth referred to as the "Grey seat"), as depicted in Figure 1. Both seat covers were made of the same material (foam) and had the same thickness (2mm). The covers were tightly fitted to the original contour of the seats. The drape covers used to conceal the visual design were made out of white cotton cloth sheet. Both seats were tilted at an angle of 21° throughout the experiment and participants were instructed not to make any seat adjustments.

Figure 2. Diagrammatic representation of the experimental procedure employed including metrics.

Procedure and measures

The seats were tested in a laboratory environment under static conditions in four stages (see Figure 1). In line with Helander's (2003) suggestion, participants were asked to make comparisons of the seats subsequently one after the other in order to improve discriminability by reducing the impact of reliance on participants' memory. The participants were not allowed to manipulate the position of the seats in anyway or use their hands to touch the seats in order to control for haptic or tactile sensations.

In the first stage, the seats were concealed with white cotton drapes. Participants were invited to sit on each of the concealed seats for one minute and were asked to indicate which of the two seats they preferred (i.e. forced-choice paradigm) in terms of seating comfort (see also Mergl et al., 2008). Participants were also asked to rate their "overall comfort" on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from "Not at All" to "Extremely" during the seated time period. In the second stage, the above procedure was repeated but this time with the seats uncovered exposing the visual design. To avoid any order effects, half the participants were asked to evaluate the black seat first, followed by the grey seat. The other half evaluated the seats in the opposite order. To avoid any order effects, half the participants were asked to evaluate the black seat first, followed by the grey seat. The other half evaluated the seats in the opposite order. In the third stage, participants were asked to rate their emotional response to the different designs using the valence and arousal dimensions of the Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) on a 9-point scale. The SAM dominance dimension was discarded as it was not deemed relevant to the current evaluation. In addition, the participants were asked to fill out a battery of questionnaires including a bespoke comfort questionnaire consisting of a combination of items from Sohlman & Staaf (2006) and Helander & Zhang (1997). Sohlman & Staaf (2006) identified 17 descriptors to evaluate the perceived comfort differences between truck seats based on both visual and seated evaluations. For the current questionnaire, only the visual assessment items were used. In addition, the items "Plush" (Helander & Zhang, 1997) and "Attractive" (Franceschini, 2001) were utilised, making a total of 19 descriptors.

Gover's (2004) product personality scale was used for the assessment of personality profiles of the seats. Product personality congruence, user image

congruence, and product evaluation were also assessed for each seat design (Govers & Schoormans, 2005). The referred "product evaluation" in the Govers, (2004) study, was assessed on the items used in the measurement scales (i.e. beautiful, good product, attractive, like to have this product) (Govers & Schoormans, 2005; Govers, 2004; Sirgy & Johar, 1999). For Product-personality congruence a direct measure of congruence with four items on five-point scales were used (i.e. product is like me, matches me etc.). An average product-evaluation, product-personality congruence and user image congruence score of each respondent for each product was calculated in line with Govers (2004). Govers & Schoormans (2005) hypothesised product-evaluation (PE) as a function of Product Personality Congruence (PPC) and User Image Congruence (UIC): $PE = f(PPC + UIC)$.

Finally, in the last stage, a post-trial interview was conducted to capture any further comments regarding the seats and the perception of comfort. At the end of the interview, it was also revealed to the participants that the two seats were physically identical and their reactions captured.

Statistical analysis

None of the data passed the tests for normality and therefore non-parametric statistics were employed. All statistical analyses were performed with IBM SPSS version 22.

Results

Preference and overall comfort ratings

As previously reported by Erol et al. (2014), with the seats covered, they performed equally well in terms of perceived comfort. However with the designs were exposed, 14 out of 18 participants indicated that the black seat design to be more comfortable than grey seat. In addition, the overall comfort ratings for the black seat were also found to be higher than that of the grey seat where the difference was found to be statistically significant ($Z = -2.23, p < .05$) (Wilcoxon Signed Rank test). Thus, despite the seats being physically identical, the mere change in visual appearance by covers had a significant effect on the perception of seating comfort. It was also reported that tests revealed female participants rated the comfort for the black seat significantly higher than the grey seat when the designs were exposed ($Z = -1.98, p < 0.5$).

Figure 3. Mean values of comfort descriptors for the black (black bars) and grey design (grey bars). Error bars indicate the standard deviation (SD).

Figure 4. Mean values of comfort descriptors for the black (black bars) and grey design (grey bars) for female participants only. Error bars indicate the standard deviation (SD).

Affective response SAM

For the black seat, the valence was found to be higher (mean=6.3, SD=1.3) than for the grey seat (mean= 5.4, SD= 1.8). Further analysis showed that there were gender effects, where it was found that females were rating the black seat higher in terms of valence ($Z = -1.62$, Monte Carlo Sig, $p < 0.5$, 1-tailed, Wilcoxon signed rank test; black seat mean=6.7, SD=1.4; grey seat mean=4.8, SD=1.9) whereas for males the ratings for both the seats were the same and did not provide any significant differences (black seat mean=6.0, SD=1.1; grey seat mean=6.11; SD=1.4). The arousal dimension was not found to be of significance in terms of differentiation between the seats (black seat mean=4.6, SD=1.1; grey seat mean=4.4; SD=1.7) and again between genders.

Comfort descriptors

Figure 3 shows the mean values of the comfort descriptors for the black and grey design. It can be seen across all the comfort descriptors the black seat was rated higher than the grey seat. Statistical analysis indicated that only the descriptor "attractive" differed significantly ($Z = -2.73$, $p < .01$). However further analysis showed significant gender effects. For the female participants in Figure 4, statistically significant differences were observed whereby the items "supportive" ($Z = -2.23$, $p < .05$), "soft" ($Z = -2.33$, $p < .05$), "attractive" ($Z = -2.39$, $p < .05$), "quality" ($Z = -2.06$, $p < .05$), "relaxing" ($Z = -1.98$, $p < .05$), "I like the seat" ($Z = -1.97$, $p < .05$), "robust" ($Z = -2.39$, $p < .05$), "well thought" ($Z = -2.25$, N -Ties=16, $p < .05$), "fresh" ($Z = -2.03$, $p < .05$)

were rated higher for the black seat (Wilcoxon Signed Rank test). For the male participants however, none of the comfort items were rated significantly different. It was observed that generally females tended to score the grey seat design lower with scores. Particularly females in comparison to males, rated "soft" ($U=11$, $p=.007$), "fresh" ($U=17.5$, $p=.036$) "I like the seat" ($U=18.5$, $p=.045$), "well thought" ($U=18.5$, $p=.042$) significantly higher for the black seat. Males in comparison to females rated the grey seat particularly higher for "robust" ($U=10$, $p=.006$) and "quality" ($U=16.5$, $p=.0280$) (Mann-Whitney U test).

Product personality dimensions

Figure 5 shows the bar graph of the product personality descriptors for the black and grey seats. It can be seen that the two designs performed differently. The black seat was rated significantly more "serious" ($Z = -2.23$, $p < .05$), "honest" ($Z = -2.11$, $p < .05$), "provocative" ($Z = -2.09$, $p < .05$) and "dominant" ($Z = -2.84$, $p < .05$) whereas the grey seat was found to be statistically more "boring" ($Z = -2.13$, $p < .05$) (Wilcoxon Signed Rank test). In terms of gender differences, none of the descriptors were found to be significant for the male participants. However for the female participants (see Figure 6), there was a significant difference between the seats in favour of the black seat for the descriptors "pretty" ($Z = -2.20$, $p < .05$), "dominant" ($Z = -2.41$, $p < .05$), "lively" ($Z = -2.15$, $p < .05$), "provocative" ($Z = -2.11$, $p < .05$), "honest" ($Z = -2.18$, $p < .05$), "serious" ($Z = -2.04$, $p < .05$), where the grey seat was again found more "boring" ($Z = -2.54$, $p < .05$) (Mann-Whitney U test).

Figure 5. Mean values of product personality descriptors for the black (black bars) and grey design (grey bars). Error bars indicate the standard deviation (SD).

Figure 6. Mean values of product personality descriptors for the black (black bars) and grey design (grey bars) for female participants only. Error bars indicate the standard deviation (SD).

Self-congruence

Based on the previous studies Govers & Schoormans (2005) it was predicted that that product-personality congruence would have a positive effect on the “product evaluation” of the seats (H1). The regression results showed that as predicted product-personality congruence had a positive effect and the regression accounted for a 66% of the variance on product evaluation (Table 2). In other words, participants showed a preference for the seat with high product-personality congruence as opposed to low product-personality congruence. The second hypothesis (H2) was that product-personality congruence has a positive influence on product evaluation independent of the influence of user-image congruence: $PE = f(PPC + UIC)$. Using a two-step linear regression, we first entered user-image congruence as a predictor variable and then added product-personality congruence following Govers & Schoormans (2005) approach.

As displayed in Table 2, for hypothesis 2, the user image congruence was significant in explaining the variance to 54.5% on product evaluation when entered in the first step. However when both *product-personality congruence and user image congruence were entered*, it was found that *user-image congruence* was not significant ($p > .05$). Therefore it was concluded that product personality congruence accounted as the significant predictor for product evaluation under these conditions. However it has to be noted that for this analysis multicollinearity might have been an issue as the user-image congruence and

product-personality congruence were highly correlated for this study ($r = .765, p < .0001$).

The same analysis was replicated separately for both genders. It was found that for females product-personality congruence had a positive effect on product evaluation and the model accounted for a 63,2% the variance on *product evaluation* ($p < .005$), where user-image congruence was not significant. However, for the males, product-personality congruence was not significant where only user-image congruence was significant as a predictor of product evaluation model ($p < .01$). The relative interdependence of the product-personality congruence with user image congruence was lower for females ($r = .664, p < .005$) in comparison to males ($r = .851, p < .0005$).

Table 2. Effects of product-personality congruence and user-image congruence on product evaluation.

	Predictor	B	β	R2	R2 adjusted
H1	Product Personality Congruence	.722	.812*	.660	.650*
H2	Step 1: User image congruence	.697	.739*	.545	.532*
	Step 2: User image Congruence	.266	.283	.693	.675
	Product Personality Congruence	.530	.596*		

(Note: * $p < .001$, for step 2: User-image congruence $p > .05$)

The direct relationship between product personality congruency and user congruency in relation to overall comfort ratings were tested. It was found that product personality congruence and user image congruence were not correlated to overall comfort ratings. However overall product evaluation scores were found to be positively correlated to overall comfort ratings ($\rho = .351, p < .05$) and there was an even stronger positive relation between valence and product evaluation scores ($\rho = .647, p < .01$).

Discussion

The aim of this study was to explore the effects of visual design on perceived seating comfort and its underlying mechanisms. The results of this study indicated that the visual appearance had a significant effect on the perception of seating comfort and preference. Furthermore, the experimental procedure was successful in making participants believe that different seats were being tested and participants were unaware of the underlying hypothesis (Erol, Diels, Shippen, Richards, & Johnson, 2014). The current findings also corroborate the previous findings by Mergl et al. (2008) and indicate the robustness of the effect. In fact, the impact of the visual design on the perception of comfort was found to be even more powerful in the current study.

Sohlman and Staaf (2006) who investigated comfort factors for truck seats correlated the perception of seating comfort as rated on the basis of the visual appearance and actual experience with two identical seats having different upholsteries. It was found that the upholstery material was very important on the comfort preference and on the correlated factors in between the visual assessment and the seated assessment. However, the shortcoming of their approach was that the designs were visible to participants throughout the trials which meant an unbiased performance rating of the overall comfort factors were not available. Also the participants were not asked for a preference in terms of comfort. To avoid this issue in our study, we concealed the designs in the first stage and revealed in a systematic manner as to use the overall comfort rating on a single scale and then apply the visual comfort descriptor ratings, to explore the underlying mechanism of the initial preference without biasing the participants.

The black seat design overall was found to be performing better on overall comfort rating, on comfort descriptors and the design lead to a higher levels of "attractiveness". This reinforces the argument that attractive and delighting attributes lead to higher satisfaction levels (Franceschini, 2001; Coates, 2002). A particularly striking result in the current study was the large gender effects. It was shown that female participants were considerably more sensitive to the visual design as also reflected in the subsequent evaluation of seating overall comfort and comfort descriptors. Similarly, in terms of emotional dimensions, the valence scores for the black seat were higher for the female participants whereas the male ratings did not differentiate in between the two designs. As suggested by Zenk et al. (2008), it can be argued that females reflecting their liking of the

design lead to an evaluation of their preferred seat with higher scores of overall comfort and comfort descriptors. (Coates, 2002).

Kamp (2012) and Zenk et al. (2008) proposed that desired emotion for automotive seat comfort were associated with average pleasant and slightly arousing emotions. As Kamp (2012) and Zenk et al. (2008) both used in their study emo-card tool to assess the affective response which appeared to be more sensitive than SAM, the use of this tool should be considered for future studies. With regard to the SAM scales, it is noteworthy that the arousal dimension did not produce any differences between the seats. It may be argued that the assessment of seating comfort results in low intensity emotions and more sensitive scales may be necessary to reliably evaluate the intensity of the perceived emotion.

In terms of product personality, five descriptors proved to be significant in differentiating between the designs. The black seat was found more "serious", "honest", "provocative" and "dominant", whereas the grey seat was found to be more "boring". A separate analysis for the female participants also revealed the descriptors "pretty" and "lively" to significantly differ between the two seats in favour of the black seat. These results indicate that the visual appearance of automotive seats can significantly affect the perception of product personality, without affecting the actual seat contours. It can be argued that with further controlled manipulation of the physical designs and particular shapes, it is possible that even bigger effects can be triggered.

The results clearly indicate that specific colours and patterns of the different seat designs affected product personality differently. Mugge et al. (2009) also found that products such as cars and a vacuum cleaners were rated as "serious" when they were grey and had a basic, robust form. Given these effects, it is of interest for future studies to understand what specific automotive seat design cues are associated with what personality characteristics. This is of particular importance given the fact that product-personality congruence is known to affect product evaluation (Govers, 2004) and by extension comfort. Again, when evaluated separately for females, product-personality congruence was the only significant predictor of product evaluation. For the males, however, it was user image congruence and not product personality congruence that predicted product evaluation. With respect to these findings, it can be argued that females were more concerned with the personality of the seat and how they identified with the seat when making decisions, whereas males were concerned more with the stereotypical user image of the seats and how well it fitted with their own image. Although a direct positive relationship was not evident between overall comfort and self-congruence measures, the relationship between product evaluation and overall comfort ratings are suggestive of indirect effects.

In the post-trial interviews (see Erol et al., 2014), participants were motivated in their comfort preferences by referring to phrases such as "I liked the

Figure 7. Proposed model for Effects of Appearance on Perceived Seating comfort.

seat”, “I felt comfy in it”, and “I felt fitted”. Mugge (2011) argued that people use product personality as a cue to draw inferences about a product’s perceived performance quality on different product variants. The participant responses in this study also are indicative of how the appearance of the seats led to perceived functional value and ergonomic quality. Participants also provided statements referring to visual elements of the seats such as the pattern and stitch which they indicated had influenced their “liking” towards the seats of their choice. This reinforces the argument that perceived comfort can only really be maximized when taking into account the “likes” and “dislikes” of consumers (Coates, 2002). Some participants referred to the black seat as “sporty” whereas those males who preferred the grey seat referred to it as “old-classical” and indicated their choice to be based on these criteria. These can be interpreted as a means of “categorisation” amongst the seats, where aesthetic and symbolic cues have led to interpretations in to classifying the seats by visual attributes.

The black seat design overall was found to be performing better in “attractiveness”, which indicates that attributes that attract the customer contribute to differentiating a particular product (Franceschini, 2001; Coates, 2002). As suggested in the Kano’s model, this lead to a higher level of satisfaction in turn affecting their preference in comfort. In this study, further support to this argument was provided, as analyses indicated that valence and product evaluation scores were both positively correlated with overall comfort ratings. These results are suggestive of a mediating effect of the “attractive” attributes and potentially moderating effects of self-congruence. This potentially underlines the mechanism of how automotive seat design is evaluated and how it might be related to comfort preference. To rephrase, we can propose that in terms of congruity theory, the higher the congruence between the products’ personality, utilitarian and value-expressive attributes (aesthetic-symbolic), the higher the valence towards the product, the more positive the evaluation of the product (Sirgy & Johar, 1999) and the higher initial comfort levels. However in order to analytically determine these effects in an integrated model, considerable participant numbers are required. The current sample

of the study is small and the findings are limited to the particular convenience sample.

Finally, the utilitarian and value-expressive attributes mentioned during the post-trial interviews agreed rather well with the six different roles of product appearance proposed by Creusen and Schoormans (2005). In particular, it was observed that comments on the design manipulations in this study were associated with “aesthetic”, “symbolic”, “functional”, “ergonomic quality” and “categorization” and “attention drawing”. Based on the findings thus far, we propose a preliminary model below (Figure 7) to explain the impact of seat appearance on comfort.

The model proposes that the seat appearance exerts its effect on comfort through the affect created. Mediation (X → M → Y) has been defined in literature as the variation in X (i.e. Appearance roles) causing variation in M; the mediator (i.e. emotional response, attraction), which in turn is expected to cause variation in Y (i.e. Comfort) (Hayes, 2013). The “affect” created by the design has been hypothesised to causally mediate this relationship as an intervening variable with regards to the findings in this study. Moderation, known as interaction, is based on the understanding that a variable or set of variables influences the magnitude of the relationship (Hayes, 2013). In this model, the self-congruence has been hypothesised to influence the magnitude of affect (i.e. emotional response) via seat appearance.

Conclusion

The study has shown that the visual appearance of otherwise identical seats, affects the emotional response, creates attraction and has significant effects on the perception of comfort and ultimate preference. These findings support Helander’s (2003) contention that aesthetics can play a significant but often an underrated role in the perception of seating comfort. Furthermore, the effects were found to be considerably larger for female than for male participants and could imply that “female oriented” seat designs can be explored to obtain the largest effects on the perception of comfort. The findings are also of relevance to the design process. Certain interior design teams adopt a, time based approach to the product experiences, whereby the experiences have been divided in to

stages: the first impression of 3 seconds, and the sensory impact in the first 3 minutes and the 3 hours driving test (Phillips, 2016). Each of these time segments form prime importance when providing input to seat designs and the proposed items to be used in a questionnaire. In order to assess the appearance factors affecting comfort, a study has to include valid and reliable items for visual appearance and the emotional response. It is therefore important to develop the proposed theoretical model on the initial impression of the seat where it might be possible that the certain dimensions of comfort perception of automotive seats are visually assessable even without seated trials. The establishment of these dimensions will provide a fundamental basis of quantifiable results on the effects of visual design cues that affect the “expected” and “initial” perception of overall seat comfort. These dimensions and cues are of prime interest for future studies.

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Bridging understandings of materials in sustainable product design education

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Abstract The following paper elaborates on the role of 'experience' in teaching materials for design in artistic design education to increasingly allow students to work and interact with issues related to sustainable design. The paper specifically focuses on two models used to articulate, comprehend and position experience in product design. The first model called 'the physical-experiential scale of material attributes' model demonstrates that material attributes are not either physical or experiential but exist and interrelate along a continuous scale. The scale includes the attribute categories: 'compositional properties', 'technical properties', 'sensorial attributes', 'associative characteristics' and 'emotional characteristics'. The second model called 'the five perspectives' model builds on a hierarchical understanding of sustainable thinking helping to navigate between different aspects of materials as part of sustainable design and provides a way to increasingly make these aspects support each other. The five perspectives are: 'raw materials and processes', 'products and use', 'service and systems', 'strategies and business models' and 'culture and experience' and. Acknowledging experiential dimensions and how they interact with physical dimensions can and should increasingly be regarded as co-drivers for sustainable design. In the paper the models are discussed and exemplified with product cases and student exercises.

Keywords *Materials for design, Design education, Experiential attributes, Sustainable product design, Experiential sustainability*

Introduction

As part of the rapid technological development, new materials get invented and commercialized, which means that the amount and range of materials product designers can choose from keep on increasing (Ashby & Johnson, 2014; Karana, Pedgley, & Rognoli, 2014; Manzini, 1989). For centuries (and even millennia) materials understanding has been based on processing and using materials with distinct properties and characteristics determined by the material family they belonged to. This was strongly influenced by the material's molecular composition and construction and information on conventional or traditional materials were somehow *transparent*.

With the present development and introduction of innovative materials and emerging technologies this transparency decreases. Whereas a nature-made material bears with it an identity from the environment it was grown or farmed in, a man-made material, or what we also refer to as an artificial or a synthetic material, does not possess the same kind of identity (Manzini, 1989; Vannini, 2009). Man-made materials, in product design often plastics made of nonrenewable resources from crude oil, obtain their properties from chemical processes and further manufacturing processes, where properties and appearances can be modified and altered in multiple steps.

In addition to newly developed 'smart' materials and novel technologies with properties and characteristics unlike materials previously known, in recent years materials that possess properties and characteristics of both nature- and man-made materials are increasingly becoming part of the market. These include materials such as: Tencel® from Lenzing, a textile fiber made of raw materials from birch and eucalyptus trees that have been synthetically processed and ArboForm® from Tecnar, a so-called woodplastic composed of cellulosic fibers from wood embedded in lignin from wood that can be thermo molded in different ways, for example with injection molding. In that sense, these materials are hybrids with compositional properties and characteristics determined by the raw material they are composed of and with constructional appearance determined by the processes applied.

Sustainable development and design education

In the infancy of the 'modern' understanding of sustainable development in the early 1970s (Papanek, 1971; Schumacher, 1974) to Our Common Future report in the end of the 1980s (United Nations, 1987) main emphasis was on ecological issues relating to unsustainable consumption on nonrenewable resources, pollution caused by irresponsible production process control and large amounts of waste. Today sustainable development is much more and the value system that defines and shapes the

concept has shifted from being mainly objective to increasingly acknowledging subjective dimensions. It has shifted from perceiving sustainable initiatives as primarily singular and non-interactive entities to embracing large and complex systems with constant interactions between human and non-human actors (Bhamra & Lofthouse, 2007; Keitsch, 2015; McLennan, 2004; Vezzoli & Manzini, 2010). The broadening of the scope of sustainable development means that more disciplines take part in a collection of mindsets, methodologies and traditions that both strengthen and dilute the concept.

Sustainable development or more specifically sustainable design is an important and inevitable part of design profession. In these years most educational design institutions have or introduce courses in aspects of sustainable design and students are increasingly required to relate to sustainable issues in their work. It is a necessary step considering the challenges the society faces today, but it also risks leaving 'traditional' subjects such as materials, aesthetics and geometry in the periphery of the curriculum.

Consequently the paper is based on the research question: *"How can design education embrace the rapidly developing field of materials and simultaneously prepare students within the frames of sustainable design in everything it can mean and be?"*.

To answer this question, in this paper two models are introduced that both highlight the role of materials 'experience'. Experience is here understood as the mental recognition of a material or a physical product (made of materials) by a person after (s)he has interacted with the material or product (Dewey, 1938; Hekkert and Schifferstein, 2008; Karana et al, 2014).

The two models are based on empirical studies in an artistic design educational learning environment and have been developed to bridge theoretical gaps in the curriculum and to embrace a holistic materials teaching methodology specifically used for teaching fashion, textiles and industrial design students at Design School Kolding, Denmark, but with focus on being applicable in other design courses, artistically as well technically oriented. Here the models are exemplified with student exercises conducted in materials introductory courses and materials and sustainability courses on 2nd semester and in on 4th semester for fashion and textiles design students at Design School Kolding (spring 2014 and 2015) and in a materials course on 6th semester for sustainable design engineering students at Aalborg University, Copenhagen (spring 2016).

Model 1: Bridging physical and experiential material attributes

The breakdown of the transparency of meanings of materials calls for alternative ways to understand materials and to teach materials in design education and the first model is used to bridge physical and experiential meanings of materials.

Very simplistically two approaches to materials exist: natural sciences and engineering disciplines focus on physical aspects of materials such as mechanical, chemical and thermal properties, while human and social scientific disciplines focus on social or *experiential* aspects of materials such as, how users interact with and relate to materials (see for example Ashby & Johnson, 2014; Hasling, 2015; Johnson, Lenau, & Ashby, 2003; Karana, Barati, Rognoli, & van der Laan, 2015; Karana, Hekkert, & Kandachar, 2009; Rognoli & Levi, 2004). Design education is influenced by all of the above disciplines; designers consider technical material properties, but just as much, designers use their perception and their cognitive experience to create material meanings. In design education it is therefore essential to provide materials teaching that encourages students to consider materials and create personal material understandings based on multiple variables within technical and experiential material domains.

To do so it is necessary to consider the value systems materials take part of. A value system can be described as the collection of values human beings and communities have developed through cultural affiliation, profession, experiences and etc. (Schön, 1983; Vickers, 1968). In design engineering practice values are predominantly of technical nature such as quality, cost, (production) efficiency and time (Olesen, 1992), while values in artistic design practice are dominated by the experience and how associations and emotions are created (Schifferstein & Hekkert, 2008). Thus only considering physical properties could mean using materials in a product that are not socially suited for the product's purpose and only considering experiential characteristics produces materials that do not follow functional requirements on for example production and durability. Consequently in a material value system both technical and experiential attributes should be considered equally (Hasling, 2015) in order not to further strengthen a dichotomist approach to the materials field (Vannini, 2009).

The physical-experiential scale of material attributes

In literature on materials for design practice a plethora of taxonomies to categorize material attributes are used (Ashby & Johnson, 2014; Bang, 2010; Karana, 2009; Rognoli, 2004; van Kesteren, 2008). Based on these, a continuous span ranging from physical (objective) attributes in one extreme to experiential (subjective) attributes to the other extreme has been proposed in a model (Hasling, 2015; Hasling and Bang, In press). The 'physical-experiential scale of material attributes' model is used to illustrate, how physical properties and experiential characteristics are linked and interact. Therefore the model can be used to create attention towards specific attributes and how they interact and can be translated. The model includes five categories of attributes being: 'compositional properties', 'technical properties', 'sensorial attributes', 'associative characteristics' and 'emotional characteristics'. A short description of the attributes are given here: — *'Compositional properties' are physical attributes*

Figure 1. The continuous span of material attributes from physical properties to experiential characteristics.

determined by materials' microstructural composition,

- 'Technical properties' are physical attributes determined or influenced by processes and manufacturing methods applied,
- 'Sensorial attributes' are physical stimuli caused by interaction between a person and one or more materials,
- 'Associative characteristics' are the attributes related to the associations that are created based on material interaction combined with previous experiences,
- 'Emotional characteristics' are attributes related to the emotions that are provoked by material associations.

In Figure 1 the model shows how 'compositional properties' can be related to 'technical properties' that again can be related to 'sensorial attributes' and so on. These relations go both ways, which is indicated with arrows. Two overall categories are applied being physical properties and experiential characteristics. Physical properties include 'compositional properties', 'technical properties' and 'sensorial attributes' while experiential characteristics include 'sensorial attributes', 'associative characteristics' and 'emotional

characteristics'. This leaves sensorial attributes as bridge builders, boundary objects, linking different understandings of materials from respectively physical and social worlds.

Professional designers with practical materials experience tacitly link different kinds of attributes as part of their practice and even though most people in everyday life do not take notion, linking categories of attributes are also part of how products are generally assessed. A fabric can for example be highly appreciated (emotional and/or associative characteristic) because it is soft and flexible (sensorial attributes), which is due to the construction of the fabric (technical property) and/or the choice of fiber(s) (compositional property). Similarly people's negative affections towards plastics or positive affections towards wood are associated to previous interactions based on sensorial stimuli influenced by the materials' technical and compositional properties.

The continuous scale of attributes can be used to describe and in some cases forecast, how future users will respond to a material, a technology or a product. Here the Nike Flyknit sneaker can be used as an example. The Nike Flyknit sneaker has been developed

Figure 2. The fully fashion knitted sock and the assembled shoe of a Nike Flyknit Racer (sources: www.nikeblog.com and www.dezeen.com). The inlaid fibers provide support and strength to specific parts of the shoe such as over the instep and around the ankle.

Figure 3. An example of a 'network of attributes' exercise made by a group of students in a 6th semester materials course from sustainable design engineering with focus on a plastic water bottle.

as a combination of new materials and technologies that both functionally and aesthetically have revolutionized the way sneakers appear. A newly developed polyester yarn and an injection moldable ethylene vinyl acetate (compositional properties) were combined with a knitting technology that allowed a 'sock' to be manufactured in fully fashion knit and an injection molded sole (technical properties) that made it possible to develop a sneaker with fewer parts (and thus less expensive manufacturing), lower weight, higher flexibility and customized support. The low weight and high flexibility provide a high level of comfort and the shoe is easy to maintain and can be used in different environments because of the properties of the fiber polyester (sensorial attributes). The high comfort and low maintenance makes it subject to many different associations based on its use, such as running, wet feet or holidays with warm and swollen feet (associative characteristics). These create emotional attachments based on good or bad experiences with using or associations to its such as well being, chills or feeling relaxed (emotional characteristics).

Bridging physical and experiential material attributes in materials teaching

Studies indicate that often there is a gap between the competences and knowledge of materials lecturers and the interests of design students (De Nardo & Levi, 2014). Design students' skills and interests, especially in the beginning of their studies, predominantly focus on materials applied in products, while lecturers, often with a technical background, are more competent in materials science and technologies. Consequently materials courses often become technically oriented resulting and somehow disintegrated components in the curriculum. As the model in Figure 1 demonstrates, physical properties and experiential characteristics are two sides of the same coin, and therefore materials should be introduced to students as physical and social entities equally from the beginning.

In materials teaching different approaches can be taken to encourage students to embrace and bridge physical and experiential materials attributes. In the following three examples of exercises are described.

A 'network of attributes' exercise is a very straightforward way to untangle students' mental structures, based on a specific attribute. Students are assigned to graphically sketch relationship networks incorporating subjective and objective attributes. For example can 'happiness' be associated with 'grandparents', 'pets' or 'holidays'. These can again be related to senses, objects and artefacts that are embodiments of raw materials and processes. In Figure 3 an example of a 'network of attributes' exercise is demonstrated. The network was made by a group of students in a 6th semester materials course from sustainable design engineering with focus on a plastic water bottle. Here students for example link the attributes 'hard plastic' (composition), 'durable' (sensorial), 'outdoor life' (association) and 'practical' (emotional) (upper red arrows), 'without PBA' (composition) and 'healthy' (emotional) (blue arrows) and 'wear/scratches' (sensorial), 'patina' (association) and 'shabby' and 'personal' (emotional) (lower red arrows). After the exercise the students applied the model as a frame for discussing values of products with actors in a project on student housing, which helped to provide an overview and create links between related aspects.

The 'expressive-sensorial scales' (Rognoli, 2004), the 'tripod approach' (Bang, 2010) and the 'comparative scales of material attributes' model (Hasling, 2015; Hasling & Bang, In press) are all inspired by the Bauhaus School's tactile charts building on sensorial experiences through the work with various materials (Moholy-Nagy, 1947). The exercises aim at creating correlation between simultaneous ways of working with materials and techniques and intuitively navigating between subjective and objective attributes. In Figure 4 examples of comparative scales of material attributes are shown. The exercise was made in a 2nd

Figure 4. Examples of comparative scales using the attributes: 'associations to Roskilde Festival', 'warmth', 'danceability', 'suitability in windy weather' and 'water repellency' to order five textile materials in a 2nd semester materials introductory course for fashion and design students at Design School Kolding.

semester materials introductory course for fashion and design students at Design School Kolding. In the exercise groups of students were asked to order five materials with respect to five attributes being 'associations to Roskilde Festival', 'warmth', 'danceability', 'suitability in windy weather' and 'water repellency'. In the matrix, horizontally aligned scales share the same attribute, while vertically aligned scales are made by the same group. After the exercise, students evaluated and discussed, why the order of material samples for some attributes are more agreed on based on objective and subjective attributes. This regularly leads to a further discussion on the role of context and experience when evaluating different kinds of attributes.

While the previous exercises are graphical and verbal, translating emotional and/or associative attributes into physical materials or material compositions, an 'associative meaning translation' exercise creates strong links between tangible and intangible mental constructs and thus between different ways to create meanings of materials (Hasling, 2015; Hasling and Bang, in press). From experience with this kind of exercise it is evident that students commonly translate into similar physical means such as materials and manufacturing techniques and that they put strong emphasis on visual appearance. In Figure 5, six examples of material samples of associative meaning translations from the key phrase 'Drizzle' to physical material samples from a 2nd semester materials introduction course for fashion and textiles students at Design School Kolding are shown.

Model 2: Navigating within dimensions of sustainable product design

Bridging physical and experiential understandings of materials is a first step to acknowledging the role and influence of experiential values in product design. In sustainable design practice similar approaches can be taken to appreciate different dimensions and further bridge objective and subjective understandings of, what sustainable product design can be. In the introduction it was written that sustainable development faces an increasing level of complexity, which means that designers can take multiple different approaches to sustainable design. A strong interest in materials does not mean that everything should center on developing new materials and using less resource consuming materials, but to understand, how materials use in sustainable design concepts influences and may support the concepts' overall scopes.

In the past sustainable design has been much influenced by technical and economic interests, which for example can be demonstrated by the triple bottom line approach (Elkington, 1997; Fisk, 2010). It is increasingly recognized that sustainable initiatives, or 'articulations of sustainable technology' influence each other and take part of larger networks where initiatives positively and/or negatively influence each other (Ashby & Johnson, 2014; Mulder, Ferrer & Van Lente, 2011). From courses in materials and sustainability taught in artistic design education it is however evident that students find it difficult to relate to this trinity and that something is missing in order for students (and practitioners) to take fully part of

Figure 5. Examples of associative meaning translations from the key phase 'Drizzle' to physical material samples in a 2nd semester materials introduction course for fashion and textiles students at Design School Kolding.

the sustainability agenda. Consequently, based on similar observations, Fleming and Sherman have proposed a Quadruple Bottom Line that incorporates an extra pillar being 'experience' (Fleming, 2013, 2014).

The presented five perspectives model has been developed as a way to navigate within the realm of sustainable design on the basis of conversations with product design students. Wanting to and being expected to deal with sustainability issues in their projects, students found it difficult to grasp its different perspectives and levels without leaving out essential details. Several students for example found it challenging both to go into detail with sustainable design as promoting environmental friendly material processes concurrently with considering and integrating larger systems such as dealing with services, strategies and business models in projects. They felt they had to choose their stance, which made it relevant to elaborate on, how and where materials can be positioned in the seemingly ever-developing field of sustainable development.

The five perspectives model

The five perspectives model comprises the above tendencies and streams within sustainable design and has found inspiration in notions and concepts used by for example Keitsch (2015), Bhamra and Lofthouse (2007), Vezzoli and Manzini (2010) and McLennan (2004) and with an *intention-consequence* relationship inspired by Mulder et al. (2011). The five perspectives being: 'raw materials and processes', 'products and use', 'services and systems', 'strategies and business models' and 'culture and experiences' are hierarchically structured in a shell like box arrangement as illustrated in Figure 6. The arrangement illustrates, how perspectives build on and supplement each other in the depth of working with sustainable design.

In the following the five perspectives will be briefly described.

- The 'raw materials and processes' perspective refers to the environmental impacts of extracting and producing raw materials and manufacturing

Figure 6. The five perspectives model linking 'raw materials and processes', 'product and use', 'service and system', 'strategy and business models' and 'culture and experience' of working with materials in sustainable design practice.

products in pre-consumption and waste generation processes in post-consumption phases and is predominantly assessed by quantitative measures such as water, energy and chemical consumption as well as waste generation.

- The 'products and use' perspective broadens the scope of the previous perspective to include environmental impacts of consumption in a 'cradle-to-grave' or lifecycle approach adding resources consumed for transportation and while using products.
- The 'services and systems' perspective shifts focus from single products and individual consumers to larger systems of material and product flows that can be interchanged and reused between multiple actors. Still with focus on environmental impacts, the perspective introduces ways to share products and streamline consumption.
- The 'strategies and business models' perspective embraces the three inner perspectives in a holistic understanding, emphasizing economic, environmental and social sustainability in strategic design and corporate business models. This perspective also builds on a 'circular economy', where circular material flows can be used to establish a restorative economy.
- The 'culture and experience' perspective emphasizes experience as a means to create value with initiatives that strengthen the consumer-product relationship or that prolongs the lifetime with having multiple consumers.

In the model the perspectives are illustrated as rather partitioned, but in reality many initiatives overlap and incorporate several concepts from different perspectives, which highlight that initiatives can be simultaneously subjectively and objectively oriented. It also highlights that more complex aspects such as sustainable business models or cultural interventions often include less complex aspects such as raw material extraction (raw materials and processes) and consumption (products and use). As a business model eco-design typically relates to raw materials and

processes and product and use, but its value is created, because users are attracted to the idea of more sustainable products, which is an experience and cultural dependent. Similarly social innovation emphasizes experience and cultural practices (Manzini, 2015), but the experiential potential is created in the interplay between all five perspectives.

Products with holistic sustainable design approaches

To elaborate on the hierarchy and cross-hierarchical interaction, the Fairphone, a phone sold as a ‘fair’ phone, can be used as a case. At first sight Fairphone seems like any other electronic product, but the five perspectives model can be used to illuminate, how it stands out with respect to sustainable design. Figure 7 shows the Fairphone and its parts and Figure 8 shows, how aspects of the Fairphone as a company and product can be positioned using the five perspectives model.

In the following the five perspectives model is used to elaborate on some of the aspects of the Fairphone as a sustainable product design concept.

- **Raw materials and processes.** *The company predominantly uses conflict free minerals for the phone’s electronic parts. However they also admit that for all parts it is simply not possible to source all materials according to the company’s ethical standards.*
- **Product and use.** *The phone’s materials can be taken apart and parts can be disassembled using a conventional screwdriver, improving the chances of recycling parts. The phone’s battery can be removed, making it possible to change to a newer battery or switch between multiple batteries if necessary. The phone has room for two SIM cards reducing the need for multiple phones and in addition to its build in 16GB storage, an external SD-card can be used to for storage.*
- **Service and system.** *Fairphone has no physical stores, but a well-built online platform with detailed information and where users can get instant help from other users or the Dutch service team. Fairphone uses an Android OS specially developed for the phone, but it can be customized for special wishes or be replaced by other operating systems. Fairphone offers open source 3D printing files so users can customize and manufacture their own cases.*
- **Strategy and business model.** *The business model builds on transparency and user involvement. The price calculation for the phone is transparent and similar to crowd funding webpages such as Kickstarter and Indigogo, users sign up and pay for phones before new batches are put into production. For the company it ensures that production is economically sustainable and for users it gives a kind of ownership. Part of the money goes to supporting the Chinese laborers’ right to be members of labor organizations.*
- **Culture and experience.** *The Fairphone is not the best phone on the market, but the community you become part of as a user makes you feel part of something that wants to do things differently. On their blog and ongoing newsletters, users are included in concurrent developments on*

Figure 7. Parts of the Fairphone (1st edition, 2nd batch from 2014) (source: author’s own phone).

everything from fair raw material extraction, troubles with Chinese authorities and malfunctions in previous batches. Users are also invited to take part of the Fairphone experience, when the team visits mining areas in Africa and the assembly lines in China, which makes you feel part of a bigger, but still graspable system.

Making sustainable product design graspable in materials teaching

As demonstrated with the Fairphone, the model can help making sustainable product design easier to grasp and navigate in. It also provides a way to incorporate objective and subjective aspects and make them interact. The model can be used as a mental foundation for exercises introduced in materials courses with emphasis on sustainable design to make concepts more concrete and to position projects within a sustainable agenda. However in order to navigate between different modes of sustainability, students need to get insights and practice ways to deal with, discuss and work with sustainability such as in exercises with focus on single aspects or based on their own practical work. Here exercises can help mature students’ cognitive comprehension and awareness and enable students to work independently, open-minded and holistically with sustainability as a design frame rather than an obstacle.

In the following three exercises are briefly outlined to exemplify approaches to working with sustainable product design in education. In teaching the exercises are parts of a methodology, so even though they here appear as single units, in reality they are preceded and succeeded by other activities. The three exercises have been picked out, as they demonstrate different levels of cognitive learning approaches. Here the first exercise focuses on understanding, the second exercise focuses on applying and analyzing, and the third exercise focuses on evaluating and creating.

The first exercise is an ‘identification of sustainability approach’ exercise, where students are trained in understanding incentives for developing and manufacturing existing products and to become aware of some of the arguments companies use to sell their products as ‘sustainable’. The exercise can also be

Figure 8. The Fairphone used as a case to demonstrate the five perspectives model. Here the green dots indicate specific sustainability-oriented aspects of the company / product and the striped lines indicate, how the aspects affect each other.

used as a way to make students aware of the plethora of approaches to sustainable design and, how products marketed as sustainable are distributed in the five perspectives model.

The second exercise has been inspired by Mulder et al.'s articulations of sustainable technology (Mulder et al., 2011) and their networks of articulations/intentions-consequences. Here students are asked to graphically sketch, how aspects may affect other aspects positively and/or negatively in a 'sustainable approaches network' exercise. For inspiration, students can use 'sustainability lab cards', a collection of fifty methods cards to work with sustainable product design (Laboratory for Sustainability, 2013). Figure 9 demonstrates, how the 'sustainability lab cards' can be used. The exercise trains students in critically overviewing interactions between sustainable design approaches and reduces the risk of presenting less contemplated concepts. It further helps to raise awareness of the fact that sustainable intentions can become unsustainable but also that intentions that are not consciously sustainable can become sustainable in the right contexts.

The third exercise is a larger assignment, where students are asked to choose a minimum of three approaches, for example from from the 'sustainability lab cards' collection and develop concepts that embraces all of them. The approaches provide a frame to explore the potentials of sustainable design and students are encouraged to use their experience as practitioners to challenge conventional ways to approach sustainable design and to explore, how approaches to sustainability can work together or collide.

Discussion

The two introduced models elaborate on the same issue, namely translating meanings and shifting focus back and forth between objective and subjective understandings of the world and thus how it should be approached. While the 'physical-experiential scale of material attributes' model helps students reflect on, how to assess, communicate and choose physical materials, the 'five perspectives' model helps students to make sustainable design practice graspable and to become more eager to challenge their own and others' understanding of, what sustainable design can be.

Figure 9. Students getting acquainted with the 'Lab Cards' (left), examples of lab cards selected by a group of students being 'more use', 'more value' and 'aesthetic longevity' (right) in two materials and sustainability courses for fashion and textiles design at Design School Kolding.

Together they offer a holistic approach to teaching materials that increasingly train students in navigating between different disciplines and on different cognitive levels using notions and concepts used within design practice. The models can be used as means to link materials to notions and concepts such as user experience, product experience, co-creation, participatory design, social innovation etc. within a sustainable design agenda. As the field of sustainable development increases in size and complexity, the models can be used to create common understandings across disciplinary boundaries.

Conclusion

The paper elaborates on materials teaching in design education emphasizing a higher degree of appreciation of experiential aspects of materials in fundamental materials courses as well as in courses on sustainable product design. This emphasis should create a stronger interaction between physical and experiential values to consider materials in sustainable design education. Based on two models, a model that presents a physical-experiential scale of material attributes and a model that presents approaches to sustainable design as five hierarchical perspectives, six practical exercises are introduced. The exercises serve to prepare students to increasingly work with experiential attributes in sustainable design education and thus relating it to their own practice as designers.

The models have been introduced together to emphasize the importance of integrating an experiential way of thinking early on in the curriculum and to show that working with sustainable aspects can be regarded as an additional dimension to existing curricular activities rather than being something different.

The paper suggests that with the exercises and elaborate focus on the diverse ways of understanding and communicating attributes in materials and products, students become more aware of the range of and correlation between different kinds of attributes in understanding materials as well as sustainable product design. Furthermore, because experiential values are emphasized, students find it easier also to relate more technical aspects to their own practice. It can be stated that interaction between physical and experiential values is a key to understanding materials as well as sustainable design practice and thus experiential dimensions can and should increasingly be regarded as co-drivers for sustainable design.

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The material expression of new pulp-fibre reinforced composites in relation to other material categories

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Abstract To help bridge the gap between the science lab and commercial production there is a need for a better understanding of how new bio-based materials are perceived by users. The aim of the studies in this paper was to identify the material expression, sensorial properties and semantic dimensions of a group of pulp-fibre reinforced composites that are still in the research phase and how these relate to other, better-known materials already on the market. The studies involved 21 different materials, divided into different material groups such as metals, solid woods, wood fibre materials, plastic and fibre-reinforced composites in which the pulp-fibre reinforced composites were included. The materials were evaluated for meaning in a product semantic study and for sensory perception in a sensorial study. The results of the semantic study gave two underlining dimensions explaining most of the variations between the materials, Quality and Naturalness. These dimensions also had strong correlations to some of the sensorial properties. The results indicate that the pulp-fibre reinforced composites were not perceived as having high quality or expressing naturalness. They were hard to distinguish from the plastics in the study. The implications for further research and material development are discussed.

Keywords *Affective meaning, Sensorial properties, Pulp-fibre reinforced composites, New material, Material experience*

Introduction

When developing new materials, the material scientist's focus is on the material's technical properties and production aspects. But to be able to foresee for which applications a material is most suited, there is also a need for knowledge about the end user's (i.e., the consumer's) experience of the material. Without this knowledge there is a risk that the material will not succeed on today's competitive market. The material is the interface between the user and the product and a large part of the making of the product experience. The material not only provides the technical function of the product, it also plays a part in creating the product's expression and personality (Ashby & Johnson, 2010). Bio-based materials will play an important role in making our future more sustainable, and while these materials are indeed emerging on the market, most of them are still in the research phase of their development. Previous studies in the field of material experience have concluded that there is a big gap in the knowledge of how these new materials are appraised by users (Karana & Nijkamp, 2014).

Users experience a material through a sensory interaction with the material, which elicits aesthetic, cognitive and emotional responses (Hekkert & Karana, 2014). The way the user interacts with the material, what type of product the material is placed in, the combination of materials, the situation in which the

interaction take place, and the experience, cultural background, gender, age and concerns of the user, all affect the user's aesthetic, cognitive and emotional response to the material (Karana, 2009). This means that the material expression is not fixed but dynamic. However, according to Ashby and Johnson (2010), all material has a character that is hidden within the material, "a sort of embedded personality, a shy one, not always visible, easily concealed or disguised, but one that, when appropriately manipulated, can contribute to good design" (p. 82). Hekkert and Karana use the term universal meanings of materials to describe a similar quality, meanings not sensitive to individual or cultural differences or type of context. But they are more restrictive in using this term and suggest that meanings of newer materials, with a shorter history of use than wood or steel, have to be learned and therefore are more flexible and not universal (Hekkert & Karana, 2014).

New materials have no history when it comes to context of use and shaping. Users have no prior experience of the material and therefore no associations connected directly to it. This limits the way we can study these materials' expressive qualities and their meanings as the meanings will develop with use. We can try to find the "hidden personality" (Ashby & Johnson, 2010) of the material by studying it in different ways. The different meanings a material evokes are partly based on the sensorial and technical

properties of the material (Karana, 2009), and therefore it will be possible to study the meanings with strong connections to these properties even though the material is not yet placed in a product and a user context.

The importance of the different senses in product experience varies according to product type and type of usage situation (Schifferstein & Wastiels, 2014). When studying a new material there is no knowledge about the type of product and usage situation the material is going to be in. The visual and tactile senses are the two most dominant channels when it comes to product experience in general, according to previous studies (Schifferstein & Cleiren, 2005; Schifferstein & Desmet, 2007; Schifferstein & Wastiels, 2014). The senses of vision and touch complement each other in that they give rise to different types of associations when experiencing materials. A series of studies by Wastiels, Schifferstein, Wouters and Heylighen (2013) showed that when only touching a material, users describe the sensory properties of the material, but when using vision only they describe more meanings they associate to the material (Wastiels et al., 2013). In this study, the respondents use both vision and touch to evaluate the materials.

There have been some recent studies on new bio-based materials. The relation between perception and preferences, on different wood-based and pulp-based composites compared to solid wood and wood-based panels, was studied by Jonsson, Lindberg, Roos, Hugosson and Lindström (2008). In another study, wood and pulp-based composites were evaluated together with solid wood and wood fibre materials, in order to see how the tactile perception related to the experienced meaning of the materials (Lindberg, Roos, Kihlstedt, & Lindström, 2013). In yet another study, bio plastics were evaluated in two different products to determine how fibreness, reflectiveness and roughness affect the perception of naturalness and high quality (Karana & Nijkamp, 2014).

We have chosen to investigate pulp-fibre reinforced composites that are under development at the moment. The material scientists developing these materials know a lot about the technical and mechanical properties, but often less about the expression conveyed by these materials. In order to move these materials from the research lab to the market, there is a need to know more about how they are perceived by end users. By knowing more about the users' experience it will be easier to see which applications the materials are best suited for and also to estimate the market potential of the materials. We believe such knowledge will help bridge the gap between science lab and commercial production. In order to understand how these new materials are perceived, a first step would be to compare them against a wide range of other well-known materials such as different metals, solid woods, plastics, wood-fibre based materials and other fibre-reinforced composites. By comparing the perceived features of the different materials we aim to find the unique qualities of these new materials that set them apart from other materials.

Material and method

Two studies were performed in which injection-moulded pulp-fibre reinforced composites were evaluated together with other already known materials. The studies have focused on two different kinds of user evaluations: sensorial properties and affective meaning using a product semantic approach (Krippendorff & Butter, 1984).

Sensorial scale

The sensorial scales used for sensory evaluation were based on Elvin Karana's scales used in her 'meaning of materials' tool (Karana, 2009). The words describing the different sensorial properties were freely translated to Swedish. The order in which they appear were changed so that properties relating to tactile exploration were presented first and the visual properties after, in order to make it easier for the respondents to see what sensory domain to use when evaluating each property. Two tactile properties (friction and dryness) were added which were deemed important when comparing the specific materials in the study. Also added to the visual properties was the degree of visual pattern from low to high (Jonsson et al., 2008). The visual pattern was described as degree of visual variation on the surface. This property was added to be able to evaluate how the grain in the composites or the wood affected the perception of the material. The pictograms used in the scales were slightly modified by Edström and Borelius (Borelius & Edström, 2013).

Semantic scale

The descriptive words used for association to the samples were based on earlier elicitation studies on wood and wood-based materials (Lindberg et al., 2013): In addition the word 'natural' was added in order to see if the bio-based origin of the fibre-reinforced materials would affect the way the respondents perceive them. The final set of words included the following terms: natural, exclusive, eco-friendly, warm, soft, inexpensive, reliable, quality, pleasant, exciting and beautiful.

Material samples

Test specimens used in this study are shown in Figures 1-6. Twenty-one samples providing a wide range of different materials were used in the studies. The different material groups were: solid woods (oak and pine); metals (copper, brass, steel and stainless steel); wood fibre (oriented strand board (OSB), medium density fibreboard (MDF), cork); and fibre-reinforced composites including injection-moulded pulp and polylactide (PLA) or pulp and polypropylene, with different pulp content and colours (red, blue white and uncoloured). In addition, wood fibre-PLA (FIBROLON®), hot pressed pulp-PLA and a wood fibre-PP compound were included. Plastics tested were acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polypropylene (PP), and Makrolon. Most of the materials are for sale on the market but some of the fibre-reinforced composites are under development. The ones still under development have wood pulp as fibre reinforcement. The samples were cut into pieces 5 cm x 9 cm in size. The size allows an easy examination in the hands of the subject.

Figure 1. Fibre-reinforced composites, specifically pulp composites. From top left: Yellow hot pressed pulp-PLA, injection-moulded PLA with a sheet of yellow hot pressed pulp-PLA on top. The hot pressed production process gives the materials a surface where the pulp fibres can be felt when touching the surface, which makes the materials feel dry.

Figure 2. Fibre-reinforced composites, specifically injection-moulded wood/pulp composites. From top left: white injection-moulded pulp-PLA, uncoloured injection-moulded pulp-PLA, red injection-moulded pulp-PLA, blue injection-moulded pulp-PLA, white injection-moulded pulp-PP, Fibrolon®, and wood fibre-PP. All samples were injection-moulded in the same tool, which gave them all a smooth untextured glossy surface and the fibres in the materials can't be felt when touching them.

Figure 3. Solid woods, from left: Oak and pine.

Figure 4. Wood fibre, from left: Cork, OSB, MDF.

Figure 5. Plastics, from left: Makrolon, ABS, PP.

Figure 6. Metals, from left: Steel, stainless steel, copper and brass.

Procedure

Data was collected in two rounds with two different groups of paid volunteers. Semantic assessments were gathered from a panel of respondents (n=30). A second data collection concerned sensorial assessments from a new panel of respondents (n=34). The reason for not consulting the same group for the semantic and sensory examination was to avoid carry-over and halo effects between experiments. The test persons in both groups were mostly students with varying backgrounds and the mean age for both groups was the same, 29 years.

Both experiments were conducted in laboratory setting with neutral surroundings. The participants were asked to wash his/her hands before starting in order to make sure no hand cream or finger grease would influence the tactile evaluation. The participants were seated at a table with the material samples placed in a pile in front of them. They were then instructed to evaluate the material samples one at a time and indicate their response on a score sheet, one sheet for each sample. They were free to touch and

Figure 7. Test setup. The respondents were instructed to evaluate one sample at a time. They took one sample from the pile to their left, evaluated it and then put it in a pile to their right.

look at the materials as they pleased, but were instructed to only evaluate the front surface of the material when it came to the visual and tactile properties. They were instructed to put the evaluated sample in a pile to their right and to continue with the next sample from the left in order to not compare the different samples to each other. The samples were cleaned and randomized between each respondent. See Figure 7 for test setup.

For the semantic study, 30 novice respondents, 18 women and 12 men, between the ages of 25 and 39 (mean age = 29) were recruited from a population of students or newly graduated academics in Stockholm. The samples were presented in random order, one at a time. The respondents were allowed to freely touch the sample. The words were presented on a written score sheet, one sheet for each sample. A 7-point Likert scale was used. The respondent selected an integer between 1 and 7, where 7 meant that the word was strongly

associated with the sample and 1 that the word was not associated with the sample. See Table 1 for details.

The sensory study was performed according to a similar protocol. The panel consisted of 34 respondents, 27 female and 7 male, between the ages of 20 and 51 (mean age = 29). A bipolar adjective scale ranging from -4 to plus 4 was used (Table 1). The respondents were students at university level or university staff of the University of Gävle.

Results

Average (arithmetic means) and the correlation (Pearson's) between the respondents were calculated. In order to estimate the degree of agreement between the respondents in each study.

Semantic evaluation: The overall inter-individual correlation ($n=30$) across all semantic ratings and samples was rather low ($r=0.35$; $p<.05$). The average inter-individual correlation coefficients for separate scales are shown in Table 1. Only two correlations are significantly above zero: *Natural* and *Eco-friendly*, indicating that the respondents were fairly consistent with each other in rating these attributes. However, the remaining semantic attributes received rather little consensus, indicating that these attributes were interpreted differently by the respondents or had a high level of subjectivity attached to them. For example, the attribute *Pleasant* had a close to zero correlation, indicating that this is a highly subjective attribute. An analysis of variance was performed on the data separated for gender (12 men and 18 women). Results indicate some differences in scaling behaviour. This difference is mainly a difference in level, i.e. men having higher average scale values on *Beautiful*, *Soft*, *Quality* and *Pleasant* scales. Men rated Makrolon and PP to be significantly more Beautiful and Exclusive than the female group ($p>0.5$). However, the correlations between the scales obtained from the two

Table 1. Descriptors used for the semantic and sensorial studies. Data were collected from test panels in both studies. In the semantic study the test panel consisted of 30 respondents and in the sensorial study the number of respondents was 34.

Semantic descriptors	Consistency across respondents (r)		Sensorial descriptors	Consistency across respondents (r)
Natural	0.68*	Tactile properties	Hard-Soft	0.58*
Exclusive	0.32		Smooth-Rough	0.76*
Warm	0.45		Low friction-High friction	0.16
Eco-friendly	0.57*		Dry-Fat	0.2
Inexpensive	0.21		Cold-Warm	0.63*
Beautiful	0.27		Rigid-Elastic	0.4
Soft	0.45		Brittle-Ductile	0.29
Quality	0.44		Strong-Weak	0.46
Exciting	0.21		Light-Heavy	0.65*
Pleasant	0.16	Visual properties	Matte-Glossy	0.75*
			Non-reflective-Reflective	0.78*
			Opaque-Transparent	0.91*
			No pattern-Much pattern	0.78*

*Marked correlations are significant at $p<.05$

Figure 8. Mean semantic attribute scores for each material group. Error bars represent 95% confidence interval around the mean.

groups are high, ($r=0.73-0.96$) indicating similar ratings of the different samples.

Sensorial evaluation: For the sensorial evaluation ($n=34$), the overall inter-individual correlation ($n=34$) for all scales was moderate ($r=0.56$; $p<.05$). The inter-individual correlation coefficients for separate scales were significantly above zero for eight of the rated sensorial properties, indicating a higher degree of agreement for these attributes. Some of the sensorial attributes received low correlation coefficients, e.g. *Brittle-Ductile* ($r=0.29$) and *Low friction-High friction* ($r=0.16$). These attributes may have been less well understood, e.g. Friction, or have shown small amount of variation in the sample set. A similar difference in scaling behaviour between genders as in the semantic case was noted, i.e. men using higher numbers. However, the ratings of the men followed the same pattern as the ratings of the women.

In this group only seven out of 34 participants were men and thus we cannot state if the differences observed are due to gender differences or individual differences.

Semantic and sensorial evaluation for each material group

Figure 8 shows the mean ratings and confidence intervals of each semantic attribute for each material group. The different groups of materials tend to have different profiles. Solid wood and Wood fibre groups are characterised by Natural and Eco-friendly whereas the metals are signified by Quality, Exclusive and Beauty. The Wood/pulp composite group shows little variation among semantic attributes. Pleasant and Inexpensive, however, received highest ratings among the attributes, although levels are generally low. The composite group exhibits a profile quite similar to that of the pure plastic group

Figure 9. Mean sensorial attribute scores for each material group. The sensory scales were bi-polar, the antonym of the descriptor in the legend is located at scale value one. Consult Table 1 for antonyms. Error bars represent 95% confidence interval around the mean.

Figure 9 shows the mean ratings and confidence intervals of each sensorial attribute for each material group. The different groups of materials have distinct profiles across the sensorial attributes. Metals, for example, are very much characterised by the optical scattering capabilities of these materials (perceived Gloss and Reflectance) and their perceived weight (Heavy). Again the wood/pulp composites have a similar profile to plastics but with two exceptions. The composites are perceived to be patterned to a larger extent and less glossy and reflective than plastic.

Factor analysis

Factor analysis, extraction method principal components, was performed in order to identify and compute underlying dimensions of the associated semantic descriptors. Two factors were extracted in accordance with the Kaiser criterion that eigenvalues

should exceed 1. The eigenvalues showed that the first factor explained 56% of the variance and the second factor 29% of the variance, for a combined 85%. A varimax rotation provided the best defined factor structure. The factor names were interpreted by analysing the factor loadings in Table 2. Factor 1 is identified by Exclusive, Quality and Beautiful which all have high positive loadings on the first factor and we named this factor 'Quality'. The second factor is identified by the words Natural, Eco-friendly and Warm and we named this factor 'Naturalness'.

The factor scores are composite variables, which provide information about a material sample's placement on the factors, as shown in Table 3. In particular the metals have high scores on Factor 1 (Quality). Oak scores high on Factor 1 but also on Factor 2 indicating that oak is associated with both

Quality and Naturalness. Among the composites, only the blue pulp-PLA composite has moderately high positive scores on the Quality factor, while the remaining composite and plastic materials score low or negative on both Quality and Naturalness factors. The materials defining the Naturalness factor with high positive factor scores are cork, pine, OSB, oak and MDF board.

A correlation analysis was performed in order to relate the sensorial evaluation of the samples to the Quality and Naturalness factors derived from the evaluation

Table 2. Factor Loadings (varimax raw) for variables. Extraction: Principal components.

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Commonality
	Quality	Naturalness	
Natural	0.1312	0.9244	0.8717
Exclusive	0.9695	-0.1696	0.9687
Warm	-0.1742	0.8748	0.7956
Eco-friendly	-0.0684	0.9543	0.9155
Inexpensive	-0.9114	-0.3486	0.9523
Beautiful	0.9480	0.1844	0.9327
Soft	-0.5871	0.6592	0.7793
Quality	0.9567	-0.1042	0.9261
Exciting	0.9217	0.0564	0.8528
Pleasant	0.7481	-0.0825	0.5665
Eigenvalue	5.7	2.9	
Percent explained	57.1	28.5	

Table 3. Factor scores for material samples.

Sample	Factor 1	Factor 2
	Quality	Naturalness
OSB	0.11236	1.61808
Pulp-PLA (hot pressed top, yellow)	-1.40189	-0.31028
Oak	0.91192	1.56584
Pulp-PLA (blue)	0.75796	-0.26090
Wood fibre (wood fibre- PP)	-0.48089	-0.28924
Makrolon	0.14428	-0.73985
Pine	0.43162	1.77402
Stainless	1.42413	-1.14042
PP	-1.41275	-0.97952
Pulp-PLA (uncoloured)	-1.03846	-0.50581
ABS	-0.66315	-0.85679
Pulp-PP (white)	-0.71140	-0.25470
Steel	0.81916	-1.21997
Pulp-PLA (white)	-0.64588	-0.53905
Cork	-0.36073	2.09547
Pulp-PLA (red)	0.12262	-0.39452
MDF	-0.94763	1.01201
Brass	2.09159	-0.38159
Pulp-PLA (hot pressed, yellow)	-0.05813	0.24659
Copper	1.71954	-0.31975
Fibrolon (wood fibre-PLA)	-0.81425	-0.11962

of materials using the semantic scales. The factor scores (Table 4) were correlated against the arithmetic means of the sensorial ratings. Sensory attributes Heavy, Glossy and Reflective show high correlation with the Quality factor. The negative sign indicates that the negative pole of e.g. Soft (Hard) and Warm (Cold) has correlation to this factor. The Naturalness factor is related to Rough, Friction, Warm and Pattern, as well as Dry, Matte and Non-reflective (the negative poles of Fat, Glossy and Reflective).

Discussion

Sensorial evaluations had more agreement between the subjects than the semantic dimensions. Sensorial properties are more directly connected to the material's technical properties and how the users perceive the material through his/her senses when interacting with it, and are therefore more constant. The affective meaning dimension is on the other hand influenced by factors other than the technical and sensorial properties of the material. Here the users' values, previous experience etc. come into play. So a larger variation between subjects was to be expected. Some differences in scaling behaviour between men and women were noted. Men generally attributed higher numbers in their scales thus generating overall higher average values. Although the ratings of men and women followed the same general pattern and were highly correlated, at some instances the ratings of the men were significantly higher than the ratings of the women, e.g. Makrolon and PP were judged higher in Quality and Beauty by men than by women. Gender differences in adult tactile perception need to be further investigated.

From the factor analysis, two factors were extracted: Quality and Naturalness with their respective associated descriptors, Exclusive, Quality and Beautiful for the Quality factor, and Natural, Eco-friendly, Warm and Soft for the Naturalness factor. The

Table 4. Correlation coefficients between the sensorial ratings and the sample factor scores on a 2D-solution.

(+ pole)	Factor 1	Factor 2
	Quality	Naturalness
Soft	-0.582*	0.416
Rough	0.333	0.778*
Friction	-0.209	0.717*
Fat	0.194	-0.606*
Warm	-0.578*	0.761*
Elastic	-0.611*	-0.009
Ductile	0.236	-0.592*
Weak	-0.696*	0.441*
Heavy	0.816*	-0.155
Glossy	0.603*	-0.672*
Reflective	0.621*	-0.656*
Transparent	-0.218	-0.337
Pattern	-0.053	0.819*
Weight	0.675*	0.254
Density	0.745*	-0.442*

*Marked correlations are significant at $p < .05$

Quality factor was defined by the metals and the Naturalness factor by the solid woods and wood fibre materials. Both metals, solid wood and wood fibre materials have strong material expressions that are rooted in what Hekkert & Karana (2014) call universal meanings. The result from the correlation analysis of sensorial evolutions to the two factors indicates which sensorial properties underlie the universal meanings of Quality and Naturalness. Quality is associated with Heavy, Shiny, Reflective and also Hard, Cold, Rigid and Strong. Metals have all these sensory properties. Naturalness is associated with Rough, Friction, Warm and Pattern, which all have high correlations with the factor and also Dry, Matte and Non-Reflective, which are sensory properties connected to both wood and wood fibre materials.

The results also present a challenge in that most materials in this study do not express both Natural and Quality at the same time. This is something that is consistent with previous studies by Karana (2012). Oak is the only material that is perceived as both natural and of high quality. We suggest that this can be due to the weight of the material, oak is heavy compared to many other woods and the results of the factor analysis show that weight correlates to the dimension Quality. But oak has also been used in exclusive interiors, parquet floors etc., which generated meanings such as exclusiveness and quality. These are learned meanings that have become very strongly connected to this material, so that even in a context-free setting these meanings are still dominant.

In both studies the materials were tested without a context, i.e., without a product and user setting. The results of the two studies indicate that these new fibre-reinforced composites do not stand out among other materials. Most of them are perceived as neither natural nor high in quality and are ranked close to many of the different plastic materials in the two studies. This supports Hekkert and Karana's idea that newer materials do not have universal meanings. The shy personality that Ashby and Johnson talk about is indeed reserved and it is up to the designer to get to know the material and make the shy personality become more expressive so that the material stands out from other materials.

The only one of the samples that stands out is the blue injection-moulded pulp-PLA sample that has moderately high scores in the dimension Quality. This suggests that colour influences this dimension.

The results show that these bio-based composites, whether reinforced by pulp or wood fibres (e.g. sawdust), at least in the shape of flat material samples, do not have a strong unique quality that the respondents could differentiate from plastics. This suggests that other factors such as colour, shape, surface structure, type of application (i.e., product), context of use and marketing will have a strong influence on how the material will be perceived. The different ways we will come to use these materials will influence the learned meanings we in time will connect with them. This makes it even more important to make further studies on how and where to use

them. The similarity to plastic can be a problem if these bio-based composites are to be understood by the users as eco-friendly, renewable materials. Plastics are fossil based and therefore not renewable and there are a number of reports on how plastics contribute to the pollution of our planet. Therefore there is a need to differentiate the fibre-reinforced composites that are bio-based and renewable from plastics. The only way to be certain that they will express the intended meanings is to understand and study the different factors that contribute to this expression.

The similarity to plastics can also help us understand more about how a material's expression, i.e., the different learned meanings, are formed. By looking at the history of plastics we can gain a lot of insight into how the way a material is marketed and used in different products influences the way we perceive it. Plastic materials started out being perceived as cheap and having low quality (Sparke, 1993). But their use in new revolutionary products, such as the practical hygienic food containers from Tupperware, that exploited the technical properties of the material, the meanings connected to plastic changed to be more positive and high in value (Cleminshaw, 1989).

Strategies for further studies

We suggest some strategies for further studies on how to get the wanted material expression of new pulp-fibre reinforced composites.

Technical properties

Use the material where the material's technical properties will be utilized the most. These properties are part of the shy personality that Ashby and Johnson talk about. For example, some of the fibre-reinforced materials will deteriorate over time and are even possible to compost. Instead of seeing this as a drawback, this can be an advantage in products with short 'in-use life', such as toothbrushes and packaging.

Fibres

The effect on the material expression connected to different amount of fibres in the composites was not studied in these tests. Karana and Nijkamp (2014) have shown that visible fibres play an important part in expressing naturalness in the material. But the fibres in the injection-moulded pulp-PLA materials are very fine in quality and not as visible as wood fibres and might not give the same results as in their study. This is something that has to be studied further.

Colour

The blue injection-moulded pulp-PLA composite had a moderately high score in the dimension Quality, but the white, uncoloured and red variations of the same type of material did not. This indicates that colours are important to express different meanings for these materials. Further studies on how colour affects the expression of these materials are needed. By comparing different pulp-fibre reinforced composites that have the same amount of fibre, all of which have the same surface and weight but differ in colour, we should be able to get a better understanding of how colour affect the meanings of these materials.

Surface structure

All the injection-moulded material samples had a smooth surface with no surface structure in these tests. This might contribute to them being perceived as plastic. Previous studies show that roughness plays a part in the meaning of naturalness. But it is not so straightforward that a rougher surface is perceived as more natural. It is an interaction between the surface structure, the fibres in the material and the shine of the material (Karana & Nijkamp, 2014). This means that there is a need for further studies on how different surfaces affect the expression of the injection-moulded pulp-PLA materials with fine quality fibres that are not that visible.

Associations from context of use

By using the materials in applications that in themselves have associations with eco-friendliness and renewability, there might be an effect of the associated meanings rubbing off on the materials, so that in time the materials themselves will be connected to these meanings. There is a need for further knowledge on how the interaction between product expression and material expression works.

Marketing

When a company release a new product on the market, it is marketed in different ways (for example commercials, social media, product placements etc.) to make the customers associate the product with meanings that make the product more attractive to them. Sustainability has become a marketing strategy for many companies because of growing environmental concern among consumers. As a consequence we see a lot of eco-labelling on consumer goods that has to do with the materials in the products, for example clothes made of eco-certified (GOTS, Ecolabel, OEKO-TEX Standard) cotton, packaging made of eco-certified paper (FSC) and furniture made from eco-certified (FSC) wood. These new pulp-fibre reinforced composites are made from renewable resources and it would seem obvious to market them as a sustainable choice and that a product made from this material would also utilize this as part of the marketing strategy for that product. Can marketing a new material as eco-friendly affect the way users perceive the material? Recent studies on taste of food show that the same banana tastes better when marked as eco-labelled instead of conventional (Sörqvist et al., 2015). Another study shows that the light from the same light source is perceived as more comfortable when presented as eco-friendly instead of as a conventional light source (Sörqvist et al., 2015). It needs to be studied if this eco-labelling effect occurs in the case of these new materials, so that the right marketing strategy for the material is used.

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Materializing experiential visions into sensory properties: The use of the experience map

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Abstract Moving from conceptual design intentions to the materialization in product sensory qualities can be challenging. For Experience-driven designers this transition can be even more difficult, as they need to move from the abstract level of user experience to the concrete level of product features. In this paper, we suggest an approach to progressively deconstruct experiential visions and decrease the level of abstraction. We propose the use of a tool, namely the Experience Map, which describes five steps to develop a well-refined materialization and maintain a solid correlation with the initial intention. To investigate its value and challenge the approach in design practice, we set up four case studies. The analysis of designers' attitudes towards the Experience Map gave insights on its ability to provide a structure for creative thoughts, while suiting different and subjective attitudes of designers. Moreover, the map supports the integration of several different elements and the exploration of alternative design directions to achieve the intended, holistic experience. Some limitations were also highlighted by the case studies, which are discussed in light of future work.

Keywords *Aesthetics, Experience design, Materialization, Multisensory, Experience prototyping*

Introduction

Designers often start the design process with certain conceptual intentions that they want to transform into a product. They might be interested in using these conceptual intentions as guiding principles for their design, to achieve better design outcomes. Or they might have the explicit aim that users can infer their intentions from the final product (Khalaj & Pedgley, 2014; da Silva et al., 2015). However, materializing conceptual ideas into tangible products can be far from easy. The challenge is to come up with meaningful, aesthetically pleasant products that are also original and competitive in today's market. This difficulty partly lies in the nature of design practice, which is concerned with ill-defined problems with no clear boundaries, and for which solutions are never right or wrong, but only better or worse (Buchanan, 1992; Dow et al., 2010; Dorst, 2011). Several solutions are possible and available for the same design question. Furthermore, designers need to manage and integrate together a variety of factors while materializing their ideas. They need to consider marketing-related aspects, such as compliance to the brand's core values and consumers' trends. They must work within technical constraints, minding the product's functionality and feasibility through manufacturing, costs limitations and so on. They also need to take into account the experiential aspects, defining how the product will be appreciated and which role it will serve in users' lives. All these aspects limit the designers' liberty (Crilly et al., 2009) and challenge them in maintaining a correlation to their initial idea, while moving from the conceptual to the tangible, material level of product features.

We propose a tool, namely the Experience Map (ExpMap), which aims at supporting the materialization of conceptual visions of new product experiences. We evaluate the application of the tool in four design cases. In these cases, the map has been challenged in design practice with designers of different levels of expertise. In the section that follows, we will first elaborate on how materializing conceptual intentions can be even more demanding for experience-driven design approaches, and which types of support designers have already at hand to cope with this difficulty.

Materializing experiential visions

In an experience-driven approach, designers usually start out from an understanding of current user experiences and contexts of product use in order to envision a new product that elicits a specific, meaningful and pleasurable user experience (Desmet & Schifferstein 2011; Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011). This experiential vision represents their conceptual standpoint that they need to transform into a tangible, material product. Compared to more conventional approaches, these visions are more difficult to materialize, as they do not concern the artifact itself, but they describe instead subjective user experiences. Experiential visions are statements on how the user might feel when using their product, often in a very conceptual sense. Obviously, designers cannot predict users' responses to their products, as these are mediated by cultural and subjective factors (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007), but they can aim at creating the optimal conditions, through the specific design of the product, for eliciting the intended experience. For

Figure 1. The two concepts of toys expressing sadness (top) and anger (bottom) developed by Weerdesteijn (2011). The sadness concept is depicted through the interaction scenario, while the anger shows the collage created by the designer as a sensory exploration (© Weerdesteijn, reprinted with permission).

instance, Weerdesteijn (2011) wanted to create toys that “aid children to express emotions physically” (Figure 1). However, this statement gave her little information on how to materialize the object. In the end, she designed six different objects for physical education, each expressing an emotion in both static appearance and dynamic movement. Figure 1 depicts the two concepts expressing ‘anger’ and ‘sadness’. We could imagine several alternative embodiments for this design goal, but how to decide which materialization is more appropriate, if not relying on sole intuition?

Experience-driven designers can find several resources explaining the theoretical underpinnings of product experiences (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007; Schifferstein & Hekkert, 2008), and methodologies to define visions of new user experiences (Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011). Surprisingly, it is difficult to trace approaches that bridge the conceptual to the product level, thus lacking support in the transformation of experiential visions. Nevertheless, we argue that it is essential for designers to carefully shape the product across the different senses, so that it will express the intended experience at its best. All product features contribute to users’ holistic appreciation, and although products will be experienced as a whole (Schifferstein, 2006), it is important for designers to fine-tune every detail. The materialization of their experiential vision will be what actually brings the experience to life (Hassenzahl et al., 2015). For these reasons, moving from conceptual intentions to tangible qualities is a delicate moment of transformation, in which every decision matters, and on which the final success of the product depends.

At the same time, it is important for experience-driven design to maintain the connection between the conceptual vision and the final design outcome, for the

extensive investment of time and effort required to understand current user experiences and develop a solid, interesting experiential vision. To bridge the conceptual level of vision to the tangible level of product qualities, we suggest a progressive deconstruction of the experiential vision, “moving back and forth from wholeness to details” (Schon, 1983). Specifically, we identify as a valuable, in-between moment the definition of the product character (Hassenzahl, 2005). The product character, also called product expression, is a qualitative description of what kind of personality the product will express. Examples of product expressions are elegant, natural, lazy, arrogant, wise, playful, etc. The product character can be explored and defined not only by keywords, but also through explorative references, pictures, or metaphors. By means of the product character, designers are able to pinpoint how they would like to manifest the experiential vision in terms of qualities that give information on the future artifact. Shaping the product character across the diversity of senses, without dismissing design opportunities coming from less usual sensory modalities, can help achieving unexpected and sensorially stimulating materializations of conceptual intentions.

The experience map

The tool we developed, namely the ExpMap, is meant to provide further support in bridging the conceptual level of experiential vision to the perceptual level of tangible properties, integrating several aspects in a unique materialization. The tool is grounded in two basic frameworks, the Vision in Product design approach (ViP, Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011) and the Multi Sensory Design approach (MSD, Schifferstein, 2011). The two frameworks offer a description of activities that designers can carry out to design for new product experiences. Specifically, the tool couples the underlying theoretical framework of ViP with the specific focus on multi-sensory characterization proposed by MSD.

The ExpMap is composed of five levels, across which designers are supported in progressively decreasing the level of abstraction of their ideas, up until the materialization in product’s sensory qualities. Each level suggests a specific activity to explore designers’ ideas, first conceptually, then by envisioning the product character, and finally in terms of sensory properties (Figure 2). At the core of the tool, there is the selection and definition of expressive product qualities, which describe the experience in a more concrete and detailed manner from the perspective of the product that elicits the experience. Two moments of exploration (Step 2 and 4) address the collection of inspirational references, through which designers can start materializing the experiential vision. In Step 4 and 5, the tool suggests designers to consider the product characterization across the different sensory modalities, including sensory categories for both static and dynamic behavior. The categories cluster suggestions of possible sensory qualities relevant to the product. The list of sensory qualities was developed through a review of related literature resources. For a detailed description of the ExpMap,

Figure 2. A portion of the Experience Map, depicting its five levels. The map shown describes the Pulse Concept for Whirlpool by Deepdesign (Camere et al., 2015).

we refer to Camere et al. (2015).

The ExpMap has been developed through several iterative steps with designers, and has been tested in a design education setting under relatively controlled conditions (Camere et al., 2015). In this paper, we describe four cases from design practice, in which designers used the tool to move from the conceptual level of experiential visions to tangible sensory qualities.

Case studies

The scope of these case studies was to observe designers' interactions with the ExpMap in a context as close as possible to everyday design practice. Through the cases, we describe the application of the tool, its benefits and limitations and how it can support the materialization of experiential visions. We set up four different design cases and we analyzed participants' practices. Participants were recruited on the basis of voluntary participation. The timespan, the subject, and the type of design project were decided according to designers' preferences and availability. Participants were provided with a package containing the map, a vocabulary, and step-by-step explanation of the tool. In order to interfere as little as possible with the normal design flow, we did not perform a direct observation or record their activities on camera. Instead, we planned meetings with designers, during which we collected documents related to the project, i.e. sketches, drawings, notes and state of progress in the ExpMap. Document collection as the main source of data can be an effective method to study the information flow in design projects (Blessing & Chakrabarti 2009). During review meetings, questions were asked to explain noticeable facts in the documents collected, or to check for any upcoming issue in using the ExpMap. Participants were formally interviewed at the beginning and at the end of the study. The documents collected, the final maps, the design outcomes and the interviews were then analyzed in relation to each other, as presented hereafter.

Case 1 – EACO

The first design case involved a team of three novice designers (age: 23-26, nationality: Turkish, Indian), former MSc students of the School of Design of Politecnico di Milano. They invested a total of four weeks in the development of the project. Their project

dealt with designing a product to educate pre-adolescents about nutrition, an eating companion (EACO) for kids with nutritional problems, such as diabetes. They aimed at creating a device that would not feel as a medical device, thus avoiding the negative perception of being 'excluded' or 'different'. Their conceptual intention was to design "an emotionally durable buddy" to which the kids could become attached and which could follow them during their growth.

Figure 3 shows the design concept at the end of the project. It describes a modular and customisable product, with different masks that can be mounted on a fixed interactive body. The device gives interactive feedback according to food intake. A mobile application, associated to the product, analyses the kids' nutrition and their daily needs, and allows children and parents to share this information. The application supplies information to the device, it rewards children when they attend to a healthy nutrition scheme by providing stimulating positive or negative face-like expressions.

In Step 2, designers explored their conceptual intention of 'creating an emotionally durable eating companion', reflecting on the concept of 'buddy' and conducting a visual research on related aesthetics. Step 3 helped them to characterise the product as light, friendly and playful. They also described it as 'vibrant', not directly an element of product expression, but a characteristic of the general appearance. In Step 4 and 5, while exploring and defining the product qualities, designers came up with the idea of the interchangeable masks. These were designed in several variants, some of which were less childish and more suitable for adolescents, so that children could ideally continue to use the device while growing, adapting its appearance to their changing taste and style. Furthermore, in these last two steps designers gave special attention to the type of interactive feedback generated by the product. They decided to combine a face-like display with alert sounds, which would alert users about notifications from the system, such as eating time, specific nutritional needs, and feedbacks about eating behaviour. Furthermore, they were triggered by the idea of providing vibration feedback, to allow product usage in silent modality.

Figure 3. A visualization of the final concept for the EACO case study and the associated ExpMap.

In the interviews, designers reported that the ExpMap was “*excellent in allowing us to be broad and open, yet specific at the same time*”. They perceived it as very flexible, providing a stimulating structure that makes the designer integrate different sensory aspects in a holistic and integrated user experience. They described Step 3 as important “*to convert intangible values of the vision statement into physical qualities of the final product*”. About the last level of the ExpMap, the designers stated that their “*design instinct inhibited further progress in the experience map*”, as they perceived it as too analytic: “*it forced us to think parametrically and quantitatively*”. However, they recognised the potential of this stage for prototyping, “*whereby designers can develop prototypes to test different sensory patterns (...) following a methodological and modular approach*”.

Case 2 – Cloud

The second team was composed of three novice designers (age: 22-23; nationality: Italian, Chinese and Indonesian). They worked on their project for a period of four weeks. Their goal was to design an interactive weather station for the office. At the start of the process, designers defined their starting point as the “*reflection of the constantly evolving, dynamic qualities of the room ecosystem*”. The designers developed three alternative materializations (Figure 4), which differed in terms of product features. Concept A was developed by seeking a high sensory congruence, with a very symmetric and edgy shape. In this case, sudden changes in the surrounding environment

would be represented by a change in the visual appearance, shifting from transparent to foggy. In Concept B, on the other hand, the designers aimed at eliciting perceptual incongruities between the senses. This led to the choice of an asymmetric shape and the inclusion of one side made of soft material in the top, contrasting with the edgy and rigid appearance. The soft side was meant as the interface to activate the product. The sensory incongruence of the soft material compared to its surroundings was designed as an implicit tactual affordance, reminding users where to activate the product. The last concept C was characterised by a dissimilar shape, rounded and symmetrical, to express calmness. The dynamic changes of the surrounding environment are in this case represented by the production of fog in the transparent part.

The three concepts highly resonate with the visual references included in Step 2 and 4 of the map. Each of the expressive qualities listed in Step 3 is directly related to the design outcomes. In Step 5, the designers added some descriptors, e.g. polygonal and asymmetrical in the shaping category. Interestingly, they developed two tables (Figure 5) in which they summarised their design decisions, listing all the important qualities to characterize each concept. At the end of their conceptual process, the designers also developed parametric, mixed media prototypes, coupling interactive animations with physical tokens. The scope of this prototyping activity was “*to explore which dynamic behaviour would better embody the*

Figure 4. Renderings of the three alternative materializations for the Cloud case study and its relative ExpMap.

desired interaction with the product”.

During the interviews, the designers reported that at the beginning of the project, they were doubtful about possible limitations to their creativity coming from the systematic structure of the ExpMap. However, “the map revealed to be very useful to punctually identify all the sensory and dynamic characteristics, and to manage the complexity of a multisensory process”. They described some difficulties, for example in retrieving appropriate pictures during Step 2 and 4. They also struggled in specifying and differentiating the alternative patterns, for which purpose they developed the matrix of Figure 5. Their need was to have “the sensory characteristics ready at hand, easy to compare and distinguish from each other”. Lastly, they were satisfied by the ExpMap as “a valuable tool to support the design process, especially to tackle a multisensory approach, because it made us explore our concept more in-depth and from different perspectives”.

Case 3 – Seaside

In the third design case, a junior Italian designer (3 years of professional experience) worked on a mid-term project for three weeks. The project concerned the design of bathroom ceramic tiles. She

aimed at eliciting the experience of “lying on the sea foreshore”. The designer developed three alternative materializations (Figure 6). For concept A, she was inspired by the texture of small glass stones. In Concept B, she aimed at stimulating the multi-material tactual sensation of the sea foreshore. In concept C, instead, she wanted to represent the waves of the sea through the tile’s shape.

The map shows a high correlation with the final concepts (Figure 6): the pictures included in Step 2 were clearly useful as visual references for the subsequent materialization. In Step 3, she did not connect the expressive qualities to the sensory categories, but she clustered them by three colours. She subsequently used this coding system to differentiate between the alternative patterns in Step 5. She described this moment as especially important for her, because it sparked one of the three materializations: “I remember I was rating the sensory qualities and one of them made me suddenly think ‘uh, it could be also like this’. And the pictures I’ve put in the sensory exploration boxes... they were supporting this new idea”.

Soon at the beginning of the project, she decided to undertake a prototyping activity by using a haptic

	PATTERN 1: congruenza sensoriale	PATTERN 2: congruenza sensoriale	PATTERN 3: incongruenza sensoriale
	DINAMICO	CALMO	EMOZIONALE
VISUAL	opalescente	trasparente	poligonale
SHAPING	poligonale	simmetrico/avvolgente	
TEXTURE		liscia	
TACTUAL	rigido	morbido/soft	morbido/elastico
OLFACTORY			
AUDITORY	armonioso/regolare	faded/sfumato	
VISUAL CHANGES	cambi di stato	cambio di opacità/luce	cambi di stato
FORCE		smooth/sottile	dinamico
VIBRATION	puntuale	minima/regolare	puntuale
OLFACTORY	evocativo	neutro	evocativo

PATTERN 1: congruenza sensoriale	PATTERN 2: congruenza sensoriale	PATTERN 3: incongruenza sensoriale
STATICO	CALMO	EMOZIONALE
<p>Objetto che mostra ciò che accade all'esterno. L'interazione avviene principalmente a livello visuale. L'oggetto assume una valenza decorativa.</p> <p>caricamenti di stato</p> <p>di senso a ruotonda</p> <p>forma rigida morbida</p> <p>caricamenti opacità con profondità</p>		

Figure 5. The two tables developed by designers to summarize their design choices.

device, the desktop Phantom© by Geomagic. This helped her to engage with her ideas and select among alternative materializations through quick, interactive virtual mock-ups, which could render also the tactual feeling of the tile. For this reason too, she appreciated Step 5, which helped her to select the parameters for the virtual prototypes in a systematic way. As the product did not feature any interactivity, she discarded most of the interactive categories (Figure 6) but she included force-feedback, so that it would help her with the settings of the haptic device. As in Project 2, the designer summarised her choices in a different layout (Figure 7), “to be more specific and analyse more precisely every single pattern”.

In the interview, the designer reported that the tool suggested a “systematic approach to prototyping. I think that selecting a pattern, rather than testing stand-alone features, in relation to the expression I want to convey (...) it makes much more sense from my point of view”. Another advantage she referred was that the tool helped her to quickly get back into the project: “it was good to make me remember the point where I left my thinking process – sometimes it isn’t easy when you are working on several projects at the same time”. She reported that the tool “asked quite a lot of time to complete – this can be a drawback in scarcity of time. Also, sometimes, the rating system was too broad and generic. I could understand that 0 meant ‘no’ for the quality (...) but sometimes I had difficulties in understanding what is ‘3’ and what is ‘4’”.

Case 4 – Designing the structure for a rehabilitation device

The fourth design case was supplied by Design Innovation, a design agency based in Milan. It concerned the redesign of a support structure for a robotic device for the rehabilitation of the lower arm, commissioned by a leading research centre in Italy. The project is currently under development, thus details on the design concepts will be precluded to comply with confidentiality agreements. The interviews were conducted with the senior designer, who supervised the project and took the steering decisions. The observation ran over eight weeks.

In this case, designers were predominantly focusing

on the styling and aesthetics of the structure, to provide users with a higher comfort. The intended user experience was identified as the “feeling of training for personal fitness”, in contrast to the perception of interacting with a medical device. As designers started using the tool only few weeks after starting the project, and not at the very beginning, they used the map to identify alternative product characters and organise their creative thoughts. Thus, they decided to develop four maps, differentiating them only in the last two levels (Figure 8), according to each product expression. The four product characters that they selected in Step 3 were ‘framing’, ‘sporty’, ‘natural’, ‘medical’. As a design studio, they already worked with libraries of inspirational references, including pictures, design cases, material samples, which they normally consult for every project. Their activity in Step 4 focused mainly on selecting, clustering and organising some of the visual references they already had at hand. However, they included several other pictures at the bottom of each map. Step 5 was detailed and different for each specific character (see Figure 8).

In this case, the ExpMap was used with lower engagement by the design team. However the interviews provided meaningful designers’ feedback, especially as they show a design expert’s account of the tool. In the interview before starting the project, the senior designer explained that “the map seems a bit over-structured to me... actually I think that my thinking process is lighter. (...) When I see the image of a Nike Air, I know intuitively the direction I want my design to go towards... If I take the picture, and I write ‘sporty’, my fellow and I already know what we are referring to. We know that all the textile part will be made of 3D textiles, that the part next to it will be of soft foam and that the structure will be a frame wrapped in a membrane. Then it becomes only a matter of detailing”. During the review meetings, the designers explained that they had difficulties understanding how to use the ExpMap for complex products, such as the support structure they design, which is composed of several parts. They then decided to use it as a general guide, commenting that: “otherwise, we could have gone on endlessly. We can move from the general to the infinitesimal part, from the shell to the joystick to the button... It would

Figure 6. Provisional visualizations of the three alternatives for the project Seaside and the corresponding ExpMap.

PATTERN A
"GLASS STONES"

VISUAL	transparent	3	vetro sabbiato (levigato superficialmente e opaco, non completamente trasparente) + ceramica smaltata lucida	
	glossy	2		
	bright	0		
	high color contrast	0		
	vivid colors	1		
	colorful	1		
	SHAPING	balanced		
massive		0		
discontinuous		1		
regular		0		
rounded		1		
organic		2		
many materials		1		
decorative joining		0		

Figure 7. A portion of the table summarizing the designers' choices for concept A.

Figure 8. Two of the four maps developed by designers for Case 4: the one associated to the character 'framing' (left) and the one associated to 'medical' (right).

become a hypertrophic explosion, and when do I stop? I could find myself designing the screw”.

General discussion

The four cases showed that the ExpMap helped designers in pursuing the materialization of their conceptual intentions with a deliberate approach. In almost all the cases, the map was flexible enough to adapt to the diversity of participants' design flows and attitudes. In Cases 1-3, designers were highly satisfied by the tool, as they identified several benefits. The cases show that the ExpMap has a *descriptive* nature, rather than a *prescriptive* one. Hence, it did not tell designers *what* to design starting from an experiential vision, but rather *how* they can do it. It suggested a sequence of activities, but designers acted creatively within these suggestions. This is evident, for example, in the different ways of approaching Step 3, the selection of expression. For example, the designer of Case 3 worked through Step 2 and 3 simultaneously.

Another evident benefit of the ExpMap was the ability to support the integration of different sensory clues in a holistic experience. In Cases 2 and 3, for example, designers achieved very diverse design alternatives by selecting different patterns of sensory qualities. The design outcomes were developed in all cases with a direct relation between initial vision and the outcome. The ExpMap helped designers in seeking this correlation, even if they are not necessarily aiming at making users infer their intentions. The purpose of maintaining a correlation can be to facilitate the materialization and to bridge the gap between the

abstract, conceptual level of ideas and the tangible level of products. Moreover, the ExpMap allowed the breakdown of the same experiential vision into alternative design directions, while visually showing designers' thinking process. As it appears from their feedback, the tool has a unique strength in providing a structure to organize creative thoughts altogether and generate purposeful relationships among them. Furthermore, once completed, the map is highly stimulating, rich in the variety of inspirations, and holistically integrated.

Some remarks should concern designers' lower engagement in Case 4. It seems that in this project, the ExpMap did not contribute significantly to the normal flow of designers. We interpret this result in light of few contextual factors. First of all, due to logistic reasons, the usage of the tool started when the conceptual stages were already advanced. This limited the tool's utility, as the stepwise progression is at the core of the ExpMap. Secondly, participants of this case belonged to a design studio with a solid and well-defined methodology, which is part of the studio's DNA. Because the ExpMap strongly encourages designers to explore alternative practices, we can observe some reluctance in using the map, since it interfered with their established way of working, their everyday habits and thinking modality. It is possible to speculate then that the ExpMap may be more interesting for novice designers, who are instead in need of guidance and support for decision-making. Further studies aimed at investigating this aspect would be needed to confirm this hypothesis.

A noticeable occurrence in the case studies is that designers started with very different types of vision statements. Most of them did not achieve a well-defined description of the experience they intended to elicit with a user. Some statements referred to product characteristics (Case 2), interaction qualities, or used a metaphor (Case 3) instead of pinpointing the intended feelings of targeted users. This indicates somehow that they struggle in developing a clear statement and in distinguishing between the different stages in the tool. Designers should be supported in reflecting on their conceptual intention in order to develop an understanding of whether they are concerned with the experience, the interaction or the product level (Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011). Implementing this aspect, we expect designers to have a greater awareness of their starting point, and consequently of how to use the map.

From these cases, we could also observe that the ExpMap offers a limited space compared to designers' needs. This was evident in the explorative stages (Step 2 and 4), for which designers gathered a wider collection of pictures than the ones included in the map, and in Step 3 and 5, for which some participants created table-like summaries (Cases 2 and 3). We interpret these attitudes as a manifestation of the tool's ability to stimulate a free exploration, not confined in its boundaries. At the same time, it asks designers to purposefully select what to keep in the map, in relation to the other elements that are already present. Hence, it prompts an alternation of divergent and convergent thinking modalities, which is a favourable dichotomy for conceptual design process (Ulrich & Eppinger, 1995; Csikszentmihalyi, 1996). Developing an interactive software application could enhance this aspect, providing the possibility to dive into each specific step, and then come back at the general outlook offered by the ExpMap.

Lastly, the results supply meaningful matter to fuel a discussion on Experience Prototyping (Buchenau & Fulton-Suri, 2000). With this term, we refer to the practice of prototyping for an experience-driven design process. The focus of this process is not necessarily on creating a 'first-of-a-kind' artefact, simulating the design concept as realistically as possible. Instead, Experience Prototyping can focus on the context of product use, on the interaction with it, or on how users might perceive the product. Hence, it often involves rough, quick mock-ups that are useful in the conceptual stages of the design process. Experience Prototyping might be conducted even without a physical artefact, but with scenarios, sketches, or any other means (Buxton, 2007; Buchenau & Fulton-Suri, 2000). Although the debate over the concepts of Prototyping and Experience Prototyping seems vivid (Yang, 2005; Lim et al., 2008; Gerber & Carroll, 2012; Jensen et al. 2015) the fundamental question on how (and if) designers can prototype the user experience remains largely open. In some of the cases narrated in this paper, the designers engaged in activities similar to Experience Prototyping. They developed alternative design directions throughout the levels of the map, and built prototypes based on the decisions taken in Step 5. These prototypes are

parametric, since they can be described in terms of the variables composing them, but they are also a direct manifestation of specific experience scenario and a product character. Participants of these case studies especially appreciated the support given by the map in this activity. By offering a solid connection between the experiential vision and the materialization, the Experience Map can help designers to think simultaneously at the micro-level of sensory qualities and at the macro-level of integrated user experience. This would, ultimately, foster an understanding on how the conceptual, experiential vision can be materialized in terms of tangible product features.

Conclusions

In this paper, we addressed the problem of materializing an experiential vision. Moving from the conceptual level of ideas towards the selection of tangible qualities can be challenging for designers, because of the diversity of aspects to consider. We suggested that a progressive deconstruction could help coping with this delicate step, which ultimately determines the product success. The ExpMap is a tool to support this stepwise decrease of abstraction, organizing creative thoughts and maintaining a correlation between conceptual intentions and materialization. In the four design cases presented, we observed that designers were able to achieve a detailed materialization and identify several facets of their conceptual intention. The tool supported the consideration of different elements, to elicit an integrated, holistic experience. Lastly, it suggested the exploration of alternative design directions, and consequently fostered a systematic approach to prototyping. Some limitations were identified in the tool usage, such as the difficulty for designers in defining precisely their starting point, which we plan to address with future work. Nevertheless, we conclude that the ExpMap contains a large potential in supporting the materialization of experiential visions into tangible products.

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Still in its infancy: Design for co-wellbeing among different user groups

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Abstract This paper introduces a design approach for co-wellbeing. We exemplify how design enables designers to facilitate a meaningful interaction between two diverse groups of people with different pleasures, needs, concerns, strengths and virtues. Given that people meet each other constantly in daily interactions, it is relevant to look at these social interactions from a Positive Design perspective, which has hardly been done before. In the presented approach, the perspectives of both parties are studied separately first, before aligning them to create one positive experience that is meaningful for both. The identification of 'co-experience states' is essential in this process, to give the designer insight into why certain complications and matches during mutual interactions occur, and how design can be used to achieve co-wellbeing among the two parties. This approach is demonstrated in a research and design case of parents and toddlers (1,5 up to 3 years old). It builds on existing knowledge in the field of Positive Design and design for co-experience, and intends to support and inspire designers in their aim to design for the subjective wellbeing of diverse user-groups in interaction.

Keywords *Design for co-wellbeing, Positive design, Happiness, Parenting wellbeing, Design for toddlers*

Introduction

Actively supporting people's happiness is a globally growing objective, at an individual level as well as among society as a whole (Pohlmeyer, 2013). The potential role of design in this matter is yet a relatively new topic.

Our happiness is determined significantly by what we do on a daily basis, the activities we encounter, and the meaning we derive from them (Lyubomirsky, Sheldon and Schkade, 2005). In terms of happiness, it is more important what we *do* than what we *have*. However, since our happiness is largely determined by the interaction with our social context, objects *can* stimulate, enable and inspire people to engage in activities that are meaningful to them (Desmet and Pohlmeyer, 2013). This is put forward in the theory of Positive Design, a design approach that encourages designers to use design as a means to contribute to peoples happiness by stimulating meaningful activities (Desmet and Pohlmeyer, 2013). What is experienced as 'meaningful' is strongly related to ones characteristics. Most empirical examples and studies in the field of Positive Design focus on individuals, communities or crowds (Li, De Ridder, Vermeeren, Conrado and Martella, 2013). These tend to highlight individual and shared needs. In this paper we introduce a novel perspective by using a Positive Design approach to design for co-wellbeing of two individuals with different pleasures, needs, concerns and strengths, exemplified by parents and toddlers. The focus on social interactions among various individuals and their co-wellbeing is a relevant and new topic in design research.

In this paper, we introduce an approach to 'design for co-wellbeing'. We will show that co-wellbeing is supported by first identifying the pleasures, needs, concerns, strengths and virtues of each party, before aligning them in co-experience states. This step creates focused design opportunities.

We first position the challenge of designing for co-wellbeing in relation to the knowledge on Positive Design and co-experience. Subsequently, we build upon that knowledge and elaborate on a case study and the corresponding research approach we followed. Finally, a design example is provided as an illustration of this approach and its potential for innovation.

Positive design

'Positive design' is used as a collective term of design research methods in which special attention is given to the effect of the design intervention on the subjective wellbeing (SWB) of the intended user(s) (Desmet and Pohlmeyer, 2013). Here, we will apply the methodology to the study of co-wellbeing. The three main ingredients of design for SWB are: design for *pleasure* (experiencing positive affect), for *personal significance* (pursuing meaningful goals) and for *virtue* (being a morally good person). These ingredients support designers in finding a relevant focus among research insights when designing for the happiness of individuals.

Design for social interactions and co-experience

Most studies on social interaction design and design for co-experience seek primarily to design user-product or user-system interactions, rather than the

shared experience (user-user interaction) (Postma and Stappers, 2007; Forlizzi, 2007; Kurvinen, Koskinen and Battarbee, 2008). Literature on co-experience design provides useful *guidelines* on an open, empathic approach to design research. The following conditions on design for co-experiences initially disregard the involved product and can for that reason be adopted based on their focus on mutual experiences (Battarbee, 2004; Kurvinen et al., 2008).

- Ordinary setting: *at least two persons should be involved in a setting that is natural to them (not a laboratory or studio)*
- Naturalistic research and design methods: *a combination of different empirical research methods should be used to allow the participants to author their own experiences*
- The sequential unfolding of events: *researchers should pay careful attention to how events evolve over time and in context, which may hinder/enable peoples' ability to co-experience.*

These guidelines for studying co-experiences of people intend to analyze a specific situation, in order to then inform the design of specific product. When designing for SWB, the focus is much more open and includes many possible co-experiences of people in daily life. The biggest challenge is to prioritize the mutual experiences that are related to the co-wellbeing of both individuals involved.

A combined approach towards co-wellbeing

Here, we develop an approach to support co-wellbeing by combining the three conditions on design for co-experience with the ingredients of Positive Design. We analyze co-experiences of strongly contrasting people, from a Positive Design perspective. Two parties are studied in interaction using the conditions for co-experience. The three key ingredients of Positive Design (Desmet and Pohlmeier, 2013) help the researcher to focus on those insights (pleasures, needs, concerns, strengths, virtues) that stimulate happiness among the two user groups.

Designing for co-wellbeing of parents and toddlers

To generate findings that clearly apply to a dual rather than an individual perspective, we select two perspectives that are likely to be very different: parents and their toddlers aged between 1,5 and 3 years. These parties interact very intensively and constantly, so we expect to see many co-experiences to study. Additionally, wellbeing is important and beneficial for both throughout their intense interactions. Design could play a relevant role by stimulating positive and meaningful parenting experiences. We first review existing insights from psychology on the wellbeing of each party in order to develop and evaluate an approach to design for parents and toddlers.

Parent wellbeing

In a review, Nelson, Kushlev and Lyubomirsky (2013) outlined the positive and negative effects of parenthood on the overall life satisfaction of parents, concluding that the negative aspects do not overrule the positive. The authors identified seven positive

parenting elements that stimulate joy and happiness among early parents when experienced in daily activities: *contribute to personal goals, connect to other people, find purpose in life, satisfy basic needs, experience positive emotions, enhance social roles and receive social support*. These elements are useful to understand on a general level how wellbeing among parents can be stimulated. More insight into the fulfillment of these elements is required (e.g. when do parents feel connected with their child?) to understand how to address them in daily activities.

Child wellbeing

Although toddlers cannot verbally express their feelings and are not yet aware of their concerns or goals in life yet, they do already experience universal needs (e.g. safety, autonomy). Psychological needs influence experiences strongly (Hassenzahl, Eckoldt, Diefenbach, Laschke, Lenz and Kim, 2013) and for that reason relevant to focus on in our study. Furthermore, toddlers might not be able to consciously steer their behavior towards virtuous acts in the way that adults can, although two-year-olds *can* already show character strengths like love, kindness, creativity and hope which are associated with the happiness of children at this early age (Piaget, 1932; Park and Peterson, 2006). Searching for universal needs (*personal significance*) and character strengths (*virtue*) in the acts of toddlers will therefore help the designer to understand how the toddlers' subjective wellbeing can be stimulated.

Design for toddlers

Including toddlers in the design context introduces an additional challenge; toddlers are not as verbal or self-reflective as adults, while most of the existing methods to design for children address older children and rely mainly on the child's verbal feedback (Monsalve and Maya, 2015). Monsalve and Maya (2015) suggest that studies on design for autistic children are a suitable alternative to design for infants. In such an approach, the children are observed preferably in their natural environment while interacting with their caregivers, who can clarify the child's behavioral and psychological manifestations (van Rijn, 2012).

Methods

The design approach was developed in four steps (Figure 1). They are presented in summary first and then elaborated.

Step 1 Understanding wellbeing in daily interactions from a parent's perspective

Step 2 Understanding wellbeing in daily interactions from a toddler's perspective

Step 3 Aligning the two perspectives by identifying 'co-experience states'

Step 4 Identifying design opportunities to specifically address these states

In the first two steps we took a case-study approach that is commonly used in the field of social sciences (Yin, 2003). It takes place in the natural 'real world'

Figure 1. An overview of the different studies.

environment and tends to focus on qualitative data, providing rich and deep insights. This approach creates a thorough understanding of the perspectives of parent and child in daily life and their shared and respective experiences (Battarbee, 2004; Runeson and Höst, 2008). Initially, to understand the parents' perspective specifically, anecdotes of their daily life interactions were collected from them (Gaver, Boucher, Pennington and Walker, 2004). In the three steps that followed, the research applied Battarbee's (2004) guidelines for designing for co-experience: studying the experiences in their *ordinary setting*, applying *naturalistic research and design methods* in which participants author their own experiences, and being attentive to *the sequential unfolding of events* in context. To understand the toddlers' perspective as well as gain further insight into the parents' perspective, their daily interactions at home were observed on six occasions, of which the last two devoted specific attention to concerns through emotional capture cards (Ozkaramanli, Fokkinga, Desmet, Balkan and George, 2013). Subsequently, the conceptual step was taken of aligning the two perspectives by identifying 'co-experience states' and corresponding opportunities for co-wellbeing. Lastly, iterations of a design concept were evaluated in 11 sessions in home environments.

Results

The outcome of the different studies and most important insights are introduced one by one.

Step 1 Understanding the parental perspective on wellbeing

Momentary pleasures | anecdotes

In order to situate the parenting elements (Nelson et al., 2013) to real-life parenting (co-)experiences, a

probes method was used (Gaver, Boucher, Pennington and Walker, 2004). Eight parents in four families were asked to share one positive or negative parenting experience per day for a period of one week. 32 positive and 10 negative anecdotes were collected (Figure 2). Parents for example elaborated on aspects such as pleasures, family rituals and parenting aspects that are difficult or rewarding. Stories of positive experiences (momentary pleasures) were then linked to the seven parenting elements described by Nelson et al. (2013). It was found that parents addressed these three elements the most: *connecting to other people* (8 anecdotes), *experiencing positive emotions* (7 anecdotes) and *experiencing purpose in life* (5 anecdotes). The researcher interpreted these as key elements to address. One parent, for example, described her favorite family moment (connecting to other people): starting the day by chatting, reading and cuddling with the toddler in the parents' bed.

Concerns, virtues and co-experience insights | emotional capture cards

Two early families (three parents and three children in total) were observed during dinner time. The emotional capture card (ECC) method was added to the observation (Ozkaramanli et al., 2013), because it reveals parental concerns regarding their toddlers' behaviors and needs. In an ordinary research setting (the home), an observer takes notes on the expressed emotions at the moment they occur without interfering with the situation (Figure 3). In this way, the observations can be discussed in more detail with the participant(s) after the activity is finished and underlying concerns can be revealed.

Parents faced multiple challenges in their attempt to manage the situation well during the dinner sessions, such as dealing with children who were tired and

Figure 2. Parental anecdotes on positive and negative parenting experiences in daily life.

Figure 3. Example of two emotional capture cards used to identify concerns parents have among dinner time.

hungry, required the parent to multitask to cook and watch the child, making sure the child ate enough nutritious food, all in a tight time slot. It appeared during the sessions that parents often already predicted certain unpleasant behavior of their child (e.g. refusing to eat during dinner time). In their attempt to avoid this struggle they used 'tricks' (e.g. using a reward or a negative consequence) to tempt the child to co-operate. This interfered with one of the concerns mentioned by all parents: their concern to act *patiently* towards their child. Instead, the parental effort to resolve a struggle sacrificed their concern to simply *enjoy the moment* and experience *positive emotions* themselves.

Step 2 Understanding the toddlers's perspective on wellbeing

Momentary pleasures, universal needs and character strengths | observation

Four families were visited at different moments of the day for roughly two hours of observation. In all of the sessions, only one parent and one child (between 1,5 and 3 years old) were present. The researcher asked

the parents to talk about the behaviors of the child and themselves while interacting with their child. The observations took place in home environments and the researcher remained in the background where possible, while also observing closely. This exploratory approach revealed common co-experiences in young families and allowed the researcher to incorporate the existing knowledge (e.g. character strengths, universal needs) into the observed situations.

During the sessions, the children showed positive and negative reactions towards a variety of activities. The toddlers generally made a mess of everything, enjoyed climbing around on unsafe objects and were occupied exploring their world around them, unaware of any danger. Several character strengths like *curiosity*, *creativity* and *zest* were noticed during play while expressing *love* and *kindness* towards the parent or an involved object (e.g. a stuffed bunny). They eagerly wanted to do everything themselves, driven by their need for *autonomy* and *competence* while showing *love of learning*.

Figure 4. Fragments from observation sessions.

Co-experience insights | observation and emotional capture cards

Most of the toddlers required a lot of parental attention resulting in a large number of observed co-experiences. When parents had enough time, mainly positive interactions occurred. However, the child's need for *autonomy* sometimes led to struggles, when parents interfered due to limiting factors like time or patience. These struggles became particularly apparent during dinner time. Toddlers did not feel involved in their parents' activities while dinner was being prepared, and tried to capture their attention by interrupting them (e.g. hugging, making loud noises). The transition from preparation towards dinner appeared to be abrupt and therefore unclear for toddlers, who were given little opportunity to engage with the dinner setting or the served food. Most toddlers refused to eat and challenged their parent by throwing vegetables or covering their mouth with their hands. The following struggle between parent and child appeared to be satisfying for neither of them.

Step 3 Aligning the two perspectives in daily interactions

Co-experience states

The two perspectives of parent and child meet each other constantly in daily activities, resulting in both positive and negative interactions. When the needs, concerns and strengths of both parent and child are positively addressed, a positive interaction ensues. Struggles occur when their concerns and responses are not aligned. In such a situation, often one or even both individuals have to compromise, leading to friction between the two. An example is the concern of parents to manage time versus the child's need for exploration, leading to limitation of the child or a compromise from the parental perspective. Of course, negative interactions are per se unavoidable, and some of them are even valuable. Children benefit from, for example, clear boundaries. This might initially cause a struggle, but will lead to a positive effect for both parties in the long-run, such as the child learning self-control, leading to a more harmonious life.

Nevertheless, in many cases a switch towards a positive interaction is desired in order to achieve co-wellbeing. The challenge in doing so is not to 'settle' for a *compromise* of either party's wellbeing, but to *align* the perspectives in such a way that a new interaction would facilitate both parties' wellbeing.

In order to align perspectives, the common positive and negative interactions that occur among early families should first be summarized and connected to the insights on the three ingredients of Positive Design. This is not always straight-forward; parents and toddlers share positive and negative interactions, and yet these interactions do not necessarily share the same content. One child might be a pleasant eater compared to other toddlers, while on the other hand experiencing more difficulties controlling his/her anger while playing. In the aim to design for a majority of early families, we searched for interaction patterns that occur with many parents and toddlers.

By abstracting the description of the interactions (e.g. limiting, challenging, connecting) we identified a set of general 'co-experience states'. Each state represents many daily situations where the two perspectives meet in a similar way. Following this approach, three negative and three positive general co-experience states were identified in the context of early parenthood (Figure 5). The red circles represent the complications that occur in daily interactions when the two perspectives differ, while the blue circles describe the states in which both perspectives come together and align.

These states are of great relevance for the designer to understand why certain interactions occur. One example is given for each of the six co-experience states, following the order as shown in Figure 5.

1. *Parent does not feel in control - child feels limited*
The safety and health of the child is primarily important to most parents, while children feel the constant need to explore the world around them, unaware of the lurking dangers (e.g. sharp or hot objects). When parents interfere with the child a negative interaction occurs, despite their best intentions.

Figure 5. Model presenting six co-experience states between parents and toddlers in daily activities.

2. *Parent feels opposed - child feels forced and not involved*

The occurrence and order of daily activities is not necessarily logical or predictable for toddlers, who have no structured perception of time while parents need to plan things tightly to complete all tasks. This makes transitions between events very sudden for toddlers, resulting in resistance from their side.

3. *Parent feels worried/annoyed - child feels misunderstood*

Children do not always understand why certain behavior is not approved and experience difficulties expressing their needs and wishes verbally.

4. *Parent feels affection - child feels loved*

When the child's natural behavior is appreciated by the parent, who enjoys the presence of the child, for example while observing child-driven play, both parties are positively engaged.

5. *Parent feels connected - child feels involved*

When parent and child share a connecting moment together, like reading a story and romping before bedtime, a positive interaction occurs.

6. *Parent feels in control - child can explore*

When parents feel in control of a situation, for example when children play in a safe context, a positive experience can emerge in which toddlers can freely explore and engage with their environment.

Opportunities for co-wellbeing

With the overview of different co-experience states the next step is to determine how design could intervene to support co-wellbeing, by introducing an activity that is meaningful for both people involved. At least one opportunity for co-wellbeing can be derived from each of the six co-experience states. Three opportunities describe how to change a negative interaction state into a positive one, while the three positive co-experience states create opportunities for design directly (Table 1). To each of the described opportunities, the corresponding insights from the user studies on the three ingredients of Positive Design (pleasures, needs, concerns, strengths, virtues) are linked.

The aim to stimulate subjective wellbeing among the users should be leading when creating and applying these design opportunities. When focusing on a negative state, for instance, a designer should be aware to not only 'solve' the negative situation towards a point of neutrality or comfort, but to introduce something positive as well. Besides, sometimes a moment of reflection or effort is needed in daily life to overcome a challenge and arrive at a positive state. Hence, a meaningful interaction does not have to be positive all of the time (Desmet and Pohnmeyer, 2013).

The following section illustrates a design case in which these opportunities were translated into solutions that stimulate co-wellbeing among parents and toddlers.

Step 4 Designing for co-experience states among family dinner time

Dinner time had been selected as an interesting and rich daily moment to design for in the context of early parenthood. During the different studies, all six co-experience states were represented by interactions between parent and child. For each state, one example is given (Table 2).

Positive Design examples to achieve co-wellbeing

An interaction vision was formulated representing the intended feelings and experiences parent and child encounter when interacting with each other and the future product (Pasman, Boess and Desmet, 2011). The metaphor of ‘a family day outside’ was chosen; an activity where the three identified positive co-experience states naturally occur. ‘Family dinner should feel like a day outside, a moment to feel connected to each other (state 5), to feel engaged and free to explore (state 6), while appreciating the moment (state 4).’ To exemplify how this interaction

vision and the positive design opportunities can be used to turn a negative co-experience state around, or stimulate a positive one, three ideas are briefly presented. For each of the ideas the numbers of the corresponding opportunities are indicated.

Conscious dinner - This feeding bowl for the child includes a timer (that is set by the parent) to enjoy a ‘warfare free’ moment in which the parent should not pressure the child to eat, but enjoy a moment to:

- connect by simply enjoying conversations (5)
- engage with the child’s behavior (4)
- practice patience (2)

Dinner story - Frame the concept of dinner time in a way that engages children to eat (e.g. by introducing a story where each page includes a bite), to:

- accompany the child in an understandable way (2)
- emphasize and use the child’s character strengths (e.g. curiosity, love of learning) (3,4)
- create a daily ritual, a moment to connect (5)

Table 1. Opportunities for co-wellbeing drawn from co-experience states.

Co-experience states	Opportunities for co-wellbeing
1. Parent does not feel in control of the situation Child feels limited in exploring the environment	Use design to introduce structure into a sequence of interactions to manage a seemingly uncontrollable situation. <i>Addressing: safety, love of learning, curiosity, competence, autonomy</i>
2. Parent feels opposed and challenged Child feels forced and not involved	Involve and accompany the child in a way he/she understands and embraces, in order to transform a daily struggle into a positive experience. <i>Addressing: autonomy, competence, tranquility (patience)</i>
3. Parent feels worried/annoyed concerning the child Child feels misunderstood	Combine the child’s needs, character strengths and natural behavior in an innovative way to reach a desired outcome. <i>Addressing: zest, love of learning, autonomy, competence</i>
4. Parent feels affection towards the child Child feels safe and loved	Emphasize the child’s inventiveness, developments and character strengths through design in a way parents feel amazed. <i>Addressing: creativity, zest, love of learning, curiosity</i>
5. Parent feels connected to the child Child feels involved and noticed	Design an intimate moment for two, to feel connected on a daily basis. <i>Addressing: security, love, kindness, relatedness</i>
6. Parent feels in control Childs feels free to explore	Create an environment where the child can freely discover in his/her own explorative way that is embraced by the parent as well. <i>Addressing: creativity, zest, love of learning, curiosity, competence, autonomy</i>

Table 2. Examples of interactions during dinner time, linked to the six co-experience states.

Co-experience states	interactions during family dinner time
1. Parent does not feel in control of the situation Child feels limited in exploring the environment	While cooking, parents face the challenge to multitask; cooking while making sure the child is safe and dealing with their need for attention.
2. Parent feels opposed and challenged Child feels forced and not involved	Toddlers can feel forced into eating food they are unfamiliar with. In the parent’s attempt to manage the situation well and feed the child within a certain time slot, patience easily runs out.
3. Parent feels worried/annoyed concerning the child Child feels misunderstood	Toddlers tend to be messy eaters and draw attention in a noisy way, which is often not appreciated by the parents.
4. Parent feels affection towards the child Child feels safe and loved	When toddlers are allowed to help out with small tasks, they feel important and proudly show their skills to their parent.
5. Parent feels connected to the child Child feels involved and noticed	The activity of eating provides the opportunity to connect, simply by chatting and being together.
6. Parent feels in control Childs feels free to explore	Children enjoy exploring with hands and mouth, which creates a positive interaction when parents allow this and engage with it.

Figure 6. Example to support parental patience during dinner time.

Figure 7. Example to engage toddlers to eat in a way they embrace.

Figure 8. Example to engage toddlers in the process of cooking with their parent.

Figure 9. The product set Kookid enables the involvement of toddlers in the kitchen.

Cooking together - Simple and safe cooking tools for toddlers can facilitate a friendly cooking environment to:

- make parents feel in control while cooking (1)
- involve the child and make the dinner ritual more understandable (2)
- use child's strengths (e.g. autonomy, competence) and behavior (e.g. hitting, pounding) (3)
- create the opportunity for parents to observe (4)
- create a moment to connect over cooking (5)
- create a safe environment to explore (6)

Kookid | The meaningful activity of cooking together
The activity of cooking together addresses a great variety of opportunities for co-wellbeing and was further developed in three iterations. The different elements were optimized in the facilitation of simple cooking actions like cutting, mashing and cracking food. All parts were designed to fit together in multiple ways to stimulate explorative use.

Figure 10. Testing the activity of cooking together with early families, facilitated by Kookid.

Experiencing the meaningful activity of cooking together

The activity of cooking, supported iterations of Kookid, was tested with eleven early families during dinner time. The parents were asked to open and briefly explore the package of product parts together with their child and give the child a small task to do, like cutting the mushrooms. The researcher did not interfere during the study. After each session, the parents evaluated the activity and product (verbally and/or through a survey). They were asked to, among other things, point out on a scale of one to seven how *connected* they felt towards their child, to what extent the child showed *explorative usage* and how *involved* their child felt in the activity of cooking.

Creating a moment to connect - All parents showed patience towards their child and mainly described the activity as 'fun' and 'cozy'. One parent said 'It is nice to work together on a project, he felt proud of helping. It made me realize we should involve him more.' Other parents commented that the involvement was nice, but that they would usually have no time to let the child participate.

Creating a safe environment to explore - Involving toddlers through Kookid created a safe environment for them to explore the different product parts and pieces of food. The children embraced the opportunity to explore the different vegetables with hands and mouth. 'It is an enjoyable way of combining education with food and cooking', noted a parent.

Appreciating the child's behavior and strengths - While cooking, the parents observed their child's behavior. Afterwards they expressed their surprise about the pleasant, dedicated involvement of their toddler and the contribution they could already make to dinner preparation. One parent commented: 'It was fun to see they easily cut all the mushrooms, that never happens! They were enthusiastic.'

Discussion

Most empirical examples and studies in the field of Positive Design focus on individuals, communities or crowds (Li et al., 2013). These tend to highlight individual shared needs. In this paper we introduce a novel perspective by using a Positive Design approach to design for co-wellbeing of two individuals with different pleasures, needs, concerns, strengths and virtues, exemplified by parents and toddlers.

We have shown that a thorough study of each side while following a Positive Design approach reveals the two perspectives. Only studying those perspectives in isolation would not have provided insights on co-wellbeing. We combined the knowledge on design for co-experiences (Battarbee, 2004; Kurvinen et al., 2006) and Positive Design. The appropriate conditions from design for co-experiences were adopted (ordinary setting, naturalistic methods, attention to sequence), while focusing on the three ingredients of Positive Design: pleasure, personal significance and virtue (Desmet and Pohlmeier, 2013).

Not only were the co-experience conditions helpful to select relevant research methods (e.g. observation, ECC study (Ozkaramanli et al., 2013)) and reveal true co-experiences, the deliberate focus on shared experiences also provided rich insights into the needs among toddlers. Need-fulfillment is directly related to positive experience (Hassenzahl and Diefenbach, 2012) as well as to the second ingredient of Positive Design: *personal significance*. For example, the need for autonomy and competence in toddlers played a leading role in the concept development that was presented.

Observing and analyzing the co-experiences between parents and toddlers resulted in six states that occur in mutual interactions which we named 'co-experience states'. These states present daily interactions between parents and toddlers in a generalized way, on the level of 'types' of interactions.

Our contribution is not so much these specific states (as they only apply for parents and toddlers and the dinner situation), but the approach of aligning interactions between two individuals with different perspectives.

The use of the co-experience states to achieve co-wellbeing was exemplified with 'Kookid', a product that facilitates the meaningful activity for parents and toddlers of cooking together. Besides identifying ingredients for Positive Design, Desmet and Pohlmeier (2013) also identified five characteristics a finished product should have in order to stimulate happiness. Briefly stated: it should be (1) *possibility driven*, (2) stimulate a *balance* between pleasure and meaning, (3) be a *personal fit* to the characteristics of the user(s), should (4) *actively involve* the user(s) and (5) provide a *long-term impact*.

Kookid corresponds to these by, for example, facilitating the possibility of new activities during dinner time, actively involving parent and toddler and creating the opportunity for children to relate to healthy food in a positive way from an early age. Yet, the product should be tested over a longer period of time to evaluate its effects further.

In addition, more research on the positive effect of theoretical-driven design and more examples in practice (like Kookid) are still needed, in order to examine the real-world impact and wider market relevance.

The example of parents and toddlers we used to present our approach on co-wellbeing was suitable because of the extremely diverse perspectives and the literature available on parenthood and wellbeing (e.g. Nelson et al., 2013;2014). While not much is known about involving toddlers in research and design, we adopted the suggestion of Monsalve and Maya (2015) to involve caregivers. It proved useful in researching how young children can be positively engaged in shared interactions. As an additional check, we consulted three experts (a child physiotherapist, a pedagogue and an educationalist) who work with parents and toddlers on a daily basis, and their contributions indicated no objections to the approach taken and the results. Further alignment of research methods with the psychology and development stages of toddlers would be valuable and will surely introduce more refinement (Bekker and Antle, 2011; Monsalve and Maya, 2015).

When designing for co-wellbeing of a different set of people, we recommend adopting a participatory design approach and looking for the corresponding co-experience states. These states will most likely be different for different projects (as they are highly context- and user-dependent). For example, when designing for the co-wellbeing of a top coach and pupil, the types of interactions that revolve around pleasures, concerns, needs and strengths will conceivably lead to different co-experience states.

We have not yet established whether the set of methods described in this paper create the most comprehensive and optimal collection of insights for the purpose of Positive Design. When designing for different sets of people or contexts, different methods might be more suitable. The methods chosen in this design case were selected carefully, and all three ingredients of Positive Design were identifiable in the derived insights. Hence, we believe that the methods used revealed true co-experiences arising from the interactions observed in context.

Further research and practice on the systematic development of the concept of co-wellbeing and related co-experience states will enrich and expand the understanding and methodology of designing for SWB in social contexts.

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Positive emotions for inciting behavior - Playing with paintings to enhance museum experiences

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Abstract In this paper we propose a new design approach in which positive emotional experiences are used to incite desirable behaviors, based on the insight that specific experiences can motivate particular behaviors. In the approach, designers first identify users' concerns and expectations and deduce from those the psychological needs that underlie them. Positive emotions are then sought that match the identified psychological needs. The positive emotions with their related thought-action tendencies then inspire the designer to formulate design intentions in terms of experiences and behaviors to target for, aimed at guiding the design process. The approach was developed for, and applied to a design case for the Mauritshuis, a museum for classical art in the Hague, the Netherlands. An app was developed for engaging a new target group of young adult travelers: to enhance their art appreciation and to motivate them to explore the local Dutch culture. We explain the various phases including user studies, generating ideas and testing designs, and discuss our experiences with applying this approach.

Keywords *Museum experience, Design for emotions, Positive emotions, Persuasive design, Design for behavioral change*

Introduction

In the field of persuasive technology design research many approaches have been proposed to support designers in influencing the user's behavior through designs that evoke specific experiences. For example, in gamification approaches, game elements such as challenge are used for motivating users to perform particular behaviors (e.g., Blohm & Leimeister, 2013). More in general, Fogg's Behavior Model (2009), explains that people perform specific behaviors if three factors occur at the same time, namely if they: (1) have sufficient motivation, (2) have the ability to perform, and (3) are triggered to show the behavior. One of the insights from Fogg's model with respect to user experience is that people can be motivated to perform the behavior if it provides them with positive emotional experiences, such as pleasure, hope or social acceptance (or their negative counterparts).

In this paper, we focus on the role of positive emotions in influencing user behavior. According to Frijda (2007) emotions differ in terms of their impact on people's perceptions, thoughts and behaviors. For instance, amusement stimulates a person to play socially and share the joviality (Gervais & Wilson, 2005) and courage stimulates to be persistent and continue a certain behavior in the face of a setback. It has been found that people can experience a wide variety of positive emotions when interacting with products, such as pride, relief, desire, and anticipation (Desmet 2008; 2012), and different positive emotions may trigger different user behaviors. A product that evokes surprise draws a person's attention and makes itself more recognizable (Ludden, Schifferstein & Hekkert,

2008), whereas a product that evokes fascination stimulates the user to explore its features and functions (Yoon, Desmet & van der Helm, 2012). These previous studies give insights into the behavioral effects of positive emotions on human-product interactions, but they tend to focus on one or two positive emotions in isolation and do not explain how differentiated positive emotions can be used to deliberately motivate particular behaviors.

In the present paper, we explore a new approach to designing for nuanced positive emotions based on Fogg's (2009) claim that experiences can motivate particular behaviors. We will illustrate and reflect on the approach through a design case that focuses on creating an engaging museum experience for young adult travelers, aimed at improving their art appreciation and their exploration of the local culture.

We first review the relationship between positive emotions and behaviors that served as a theoretical basis of the design approach. Next, we will report our analysis of the behavior of young adult travelers in terms of underlying (abstract) psychological needs, and we will discuss how these led to multiple positive emotions as design targets for inducing favorable behaviors that facilitate an engaging museum experience.

Positive emotions and behavior

The positive impact of pleasure on behavior has been proven in various studies (e.g., Chitturi, 2009; Mugge, Schoormans, & Schifferstein, 2005; Tractinsky, Katz, & Ikar, 2000) and design researchers gave attention to

how design can facilitate positive emotional experiences. Various design approaches and frameworks have been proposed to support designers in their attempts to generate pleasurable experiences (e.g. Jordan, 2000; Norman, 2004). However, these approaches tend to deal with generalized pleasure or a small set of positive emotions, and do not explicitly explain their effects on behavior.

The reason for this may be that contrary to negative emotions, differences between positive emotions experienced in human-product interactions are subtle (Desmet, 2002; Laurans, Desmet, & Hekkert, 2012) and are not seen as directly causing behavior that is readily observable (Fredrickson & Cohn, 2008). Although all distinct emotions always come along with a particular action tendency that influences people's inclinations to behave in a certain manner (Frijda, 2007), action tendencies for positive emotions are less obvious than those for negative ones. For instance, while fear immediately makes us run away and anger makes us oppose, contentment or admiration do not spark such immediate behavior. Fredrickson (1998) proposed the term 'thought-action tendency' to accommodate the characteristics of positive emotions since unlike negative emotions, some positive emotions, e.g. hope and satisfaction, do not stimulate immediate changes in physical action, but primarily in cognitive activity, influencing physical activity afterwards.

Recently, various studies have been published that explored behavioral effects of distinct positive emotions. For example, Fredrickson (2013) compared ten different positive emotions in terms of their impact on behavior; contentment stimulates an urge to savor life circumstances and recent successes (1998), and hope stimulates an urge to commit to the activity at hand (Lazarus, 1991). Since each of these positive emotions involves different thought-action tendencies, they are likely to result in different behaviors in a direct or indirect way (Fredrickson, 2013). In line with this, we propose that understanding the various relationships between emotions and thought-action tendencies can be put to use for purposefully influencing a user's behavior. For example, imagine the task of designing a playful product that will make users jump and look over a wall that is higher than themselves and have a positive emotional experience while doing so. If a designer generates ideas for the positive emotion of surprise the resulting solutions will be different from those of designing for confidence. Design for surprise may, for example, lead to ideas about surprising things that can be seen on the other side of the wall, whilst design for confidence may lead to ideas for challenging users to ever jump higher to have a better look at what is on the other side.

The advantage of considering particular positive emotions is that, as discussed in Yoon, Pohlmeier, & Desmet (2014) and Desmet (2012), it enables designers to clarify their design intentions in terms of emotional impact upfront in the design process, rather than as an afterthought. Presumably this can increase the effectiveness of the design process and its outcomes.

The above studies by Yoon, Pohlmeier, & Desmet (2014) and Desmet (2012) not only demonstrated the benefits of designing for particular positive emotions they also provided insights into design strategies for evoking specific emotions. However, these studies tend to solely focus on emotional experiences, not necessarily taking their implications on users' behaviors into account.

In the following sections we will discuss a design case in which we reflected on the design process, and in which we explored how particular behaviors can be incited by means of positive emotions.

Design case

Background

In our design case we explore to what extent, in line with the theories of Fogg (2009) and Frijda (2007), positive emotional experience can facilitate desired behaviors in a physical context. We collaborated with the museum "the Mauritshuis" and design consultancy "Kiss the Frog" to create an engaging museum experience that provides visitors of the Mauritshuis with positive emotional experiences and influences their behaviors.

The Mauritshuis is a classical art museum, in the center of The Hague, the Netherlands, mainly exhibiting paintings from the Dutch Golden Age period (17th century), including Rembrandt and Vermeer. A study by the Dutch Museum Association (2010) showed that the Dutch museum sector would meet at least three challenges in the near future: cuts in subsidies, an increase of the number of international tourists and the rise of the digital generation. These challenges motivated the Mauritshuis to look for new potential visitors; one of these is the young adult traveler. The project goal was to design for a product-service system that enhances the art appreciation of young adult travelers and motivates them to explore the local culture.

Design approach

The design process began by investigating the current museum experiences of young adult travelers and explored positive emotions from their previous experiences as inspiration for a new engaging museum experience. To help the designers to think outside of the box when exploring possibilities, we adopted an approach similar to that of Hekkert & van Dijk (2011), proposing designers to explore desirable interactions with the product by defining interaction qualities upfront, in the form of multifaceted experiences. The term 'interaction qualities' refers to characteristics of a user's experience of interacting with a product or a service (Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011; Löwgren, 2009).

We first focused on current behaviors along with a visitor's related expectations and concerns, for example the behavior of talking to a companion with the expectation of sharing one's feeling about a painting with others. We then translated these expectations and concerns into psychological needs, for example interpreting the desire of sharing feelings with someone as fulfilling the psychological need of

Figure 1. The framework of the design process.

relatedness (Sheldon et al., 2001). The subsequent step in our design was based on the research of Hassenzahl, Diefenbach and Göritz (2010), which indicates the relation between the fulfillment of psychological needs and positive affects, and the research of Vermeeren et al. (2014) which suggests that experiencing a need may set people to action. Using the abstract definition of the desired need fulfillment, we explored the possible positive emotions that could contribute to an engaging museum experience and of which the thought-action tendencies would facilitate favorable behaviors (Figure 1 depicts our design approach).

Identifying concerns and expectations of the Mauritshuis visitors

The design process started with observing behaviors of young adult travelers in the Mauritshuis, and with identifying their expectations and concerns in relation to the Mauritshuis. The museum experience of young adult travelers can be seen as part of their travel experience. The travel purpose of young adult travelers possibly influences their expectations and concerns in relation to the museum. Therefore, we conducted two user studies to gain a better understanding of desired museum experiences of young adult travelers. The first study was conducted in the form of observations of, and interviews with 16 young adult visitors in the Mauritshuis. The second study consisted of a contextmapping workshop (Sleeswijk Visser et al., 2005) with seven young adult travelers, to better

understand their travel focuses and the association between the travel focuses and museum experiences during the trip (Figure 2). The interviews and discussions in both studies were audio recorded.

Results

The collected data from both studies were transcribed, and interesting quotes were then clustered into groups of expectations and concerns in relation to behaviors; for example the quote, *“I was wandering around trying to find interesting details of the paintings”*, referring to the behavior of looking into the details of the painting, was motivated by the expectation to discover interesting details from the painting. Thus, based on the observations, interviews and workshops, we assessed how certain expectations and concerns of the young adult travelers had led to their behaviors as observed in the museum,

In general, the behaviors of the participants could be clustered into four categories: (1) interacting with paintings, (2) interacting with other visitors, (3) interacting with the museum environment and (4) interacting with people who were not in the museum. For example, the category of “interacting with paintings” included looking into the details of the painting, listening to the audio guide, looking for the famous paintings and taking photos of or with paintings.

From the user research, we could understand that

Figure 2. The photos of the contextmapping workshop.

certain motivations resulted in particular behaviors, but we still did not know which psychological needs had triggered the particular motivations; for example, what is the psychological need behind the behavior of exploring the details of a painting? To deal with this, we used Sheldon et al.'s candidate psychological needs (2001) to make inferences of which latent needs could have been at the basis of the particular observed behaviors.

Identifying psychological needs

Sheldon et al. (2001) proposed that there are ten psychological needs that contribute to satisfying experiences and eventually to personal thriving. We clustered the identified behaviors of the young adult travelers according to Sheldon et al.'s psychological needs; for example, the behavior of exploring the paintings was considered to be related to fulfilling the psychological need of pleasure stimulation. Table 1 shows some examples of the data.

Determining the intended emotional experiences to design for

After identifying the psychological needs of young adult travelers in the Mauritshuis, we determined positive emotions that could be associated with those psychological needs. We adopted the 25 positive emotions from the typology of positive emotions proposed by Desmet (2012) and clustered them into six psychological needs we had identified for the new museum experience. For example, one of the psychological needs of young adult travelers was pleasure-stimulation. Related positive emotions could be fascination, inspiration, enchantment, joy, amusement, surprise, energetic, lust and anticipation. The thought-action tendencies of each positive emotion may then give designers inspiration for designing new museum experiences that would incite particular behaviors for fulfilling the related psychological needs. For example, the thought-action tendency of amusement could motivate young adult travelers to play socially or share the joviality, fulfilling the need of relatedness, while the thought-action tendency of pride may encourage them to reward themselves, show off, or persevere, fulfilling the need of self-actualization.

As shown above, we found that each psychological need can be related to several positive emotions. Different thought-action tendencies of one particular positive emotion (for example, fascination and enchantment) can be combined to stimulate creativity

in coming up with design concepts, whilst designing for two positive emotions at the same time may (but not necessarily does) lead to conflicting situations. For example, design for relaxation and excitement cannot be achieved at the same time. Thus, we created a long list of potential positive emotions to possibly design for, and at this point needed to determine which positive emotions to target at for the new museum experience in the Mauritshuis.

The Mauritshuis had indicated that it is part of their mission to provide visitors with a place for casual learning, social sharing, art appreciation and self-growth. Thus, we decided to particularly look into the psychological needs of competence, relatedness, pleasure-stimulation, and self-actualization, and selected a set of related positive emotions that we considered important, resulting in the five design intentions:

1. **Competence:** Young adult travelers should feel active/interested to gain new knowledge about the painting. The thought-action tendency of anticipation, joy, fascination and inspiration can trigger the curiosity of young adult travelers about the story behind the painting.
2. **Relatedness:** Young adult travelers should enjoy the social bonding with others. The thought-action tendency of amusement and joy can encourage young adult travelers to interact with others.
3. **Pleasure-stimulation:** Young adult travelers should be motivated to look into the details of the painting. The thought-action tendency of fascination, surprise and enchantment can facilitate young adult travelers to explore the painting.
4. **Pleasure-stimulation:** Young adult travelers should enjoy the cozy atmosphere in the museum. The thought-action tendency of joy and enchantment can facilitate young adult travelers to be absorbed in the museum visiting event.
5. **Self-actualization:** The exhibition should be meaningful to young adult travelers. The thought-action tendency of pride and satisfaction can encourage young adult travelers to embrace art and culture and can make them feel that they have achieved something meaningful in their lives.

In conclusion, there would be nine positive emotions involved in the engaging museum experience: anticipation, fascination, inspiration, enchantment,

Table 1. Examples of the psychological needs associated with the identified behaviors, expectations, and concerns.

Behavior	Expectation/ Concern	Candidate Psychological Needs
Listen to the audio of the paintings	To learn the meaning / knowledge of the paintings	Competence
Look for famous paintings	Not to miss any good / famous paintings	Security
Appreciate the interior and the view outdoor	Enjoy the atmosphere in the museum	Pleasure-stimulation
Buy the souvenirs	To refresh the exhibition later	Self-actualization-meaning
Share the feelings of the paintings with others	To build the connection with others in the museum	Relatedness
Post the photos taken in the museum online	To show off the unique experience to friends	Popularity-influence
...

Figure 3. Examples of the ideas inspired by positive emotions: surprise (left) and inspiration (right).

amusement, surprise, pride, joy and satisfaction. The thought-action tendencies of these nine positive emotions would form the interaction qualities of the new museum experience and would be used as the source of inspiration for developing concepts.

Developing the concept to incite the behaviors Ideation session with positive emotions

We conducted an ideation session that focused on generating ideas inspired by positive emotions that could be related to museum engagement for young adult travelers. Five Industrial Design students from TU Delft joined the session. The session consisted of three parts explained as follow.

Participants first gained an understanding of the target group (part 1), and then they started brainstorming about museum experiences, inspired by positive emotions (part 2). For part 2 we used positive emotional granularity cards (Yoon, Desmet, & Pohlmeier, 2013) each of which contains an explanation of a particular emotion. Designers read the cards and wrote down ideas based on those particular emotions, in the form of either concrete objects or abstract experiences (for example, amazing nature or eye contact for the emotion “enchantment”, respectively). After that, participants again tried to come up with new ideas, this time based on the ideas that others had written down in the previous round.

In the third part of the session, we asked the designers to again generate ideas related to positive emotions, however, now also in response to each of the five design intentions (e.g. ideas for the positive emotions “amusement” and “joy” in response to the design intention “young adult travelers should enjoy the social bounding with others”).

Brainstorming based on the positive emotions led to a variety of ideas. For example, inspired by the emotion ‘surprise’ and its related thought-action tendency of ‘being attentive’ one designer came up with the idea of “Finding funny details in a painting”; and ‘fascination’ led to the idea “comparing the old subject in the painting with what it looks now in the real world” (Figure 3).

We evaluated the generated ideas taking the design intentions as criteria. The evaluation led to the selection of two ideas. One was about an app with a ‘find the differences’ game that would encourage

young adult travelers to explore the beauty of paintings and arouse their interests to learn the story of the paintings. The stories of the paintings would include knowledge about classical arts as well as about Dutch culture. This idea aimed at inciting the behavior of looking into the paintings, listening to audio fragments telling stories about them and talking to their companions in the museum.

The other idea was to provide young adult travelers with a customized museum tour through an app that guides them to explore the topic of the paintings they are interested in. Topics included knowledge about art, Dutch history and cultural trivia. This app aimed at inciting the behavior of listening to audio fragments and sharing their feeling with friends.

The two ideas were developed into two conceptual designs for museum experiences. The museum experiences included young adult travelers experiences before, as well as during the visit to an exhibition and after it. For example, one museum experience enabled young adult travelers to watch an animation about the background of the exhibition before the museum tour started, and allowed them to play the ‘find the differences’ game during the tour and create a personal souvenir after finishing the tour.

Evaluating and improving the generated concepts

A user test session was conducted to evaluate to what extent the two museum experiences could engage young adult travelers in the museum and incite the desired behaviors (Figure 4). It was conducted with seven participants who were invited to participate in role-playing the use of the conceptual designs in a simulated museum environment with paper prototypes. During the test participants’ actions were observed and participants were provided with simulated responses similar to those they would get in reality (e.g., a researcher would manually start an audio fragment). Both designs evoked much of the desired behaviors. However, in the interviews afterwards, they indicated that the ‘find the differences’ game better engaged them for three reasons: (1) it encouraged them to focus on paintings to discover details in it, (2) it enabled them to interact with the paintings in a fun and dynamic way; (3) they liked the idea that the story told in the audio fragments was not only about the artwork itself, but also about information that was closer to their own lives (i.e., Dutch cultural trivia).

Figure 4. Photos of the user test.

The result of the user test showed the potential of the ‘find the differences’ game to engage young adult travelers. We decided to further develop it, and to include some successful elements of the other game concept.

Design of the treasure hunting app

The final design is a treasure hunting app that also contains the function of giving travel tips to the young adult travelers for exploring the Hague (Figure 5). A short movie when starting the app briefly introduces the treasure hunting game. Visitors then select a room to go to. When entering the room they engage in a ‘find the painting’ game based on hints. For example a hint such as ‘light and shadow’ may refer to Ruben’s painting ‘Old Woman and Boy with Candles’. Having found the painting, the app would depict it, but in the depicted painting a few details would be different from the real painting. The player of the game can indicate in the app, the location of the difference and would then be provided with the opportunity of listening to an audio fragment about or related to that detail, narrated by a young adult, local to the city of The Hague.

Typically in the audio fragments a story starts by explaining the painting and the depicted aspects of traditional Dutch culture, and then connects the story to modern Dutch culture. After having identified five ‘treasures’ (i.e., stories related to identified differences), travel tips related to the modern Dutch culture topics will be unlocked. For example, in the app version of the painting ‘Still Life with Cheeses,

Almonds and Pretzels’ the color of the beer bottle would be changed from brown to green, referring to the color of the modern Dutch beer brand Heineken, and one of the breads would be changed into a bread roll with a Dutch ‘kroket’ (popular meat snack) with the travel tip explaining where to get such a snack.

Evaluating the app

We evaluated the app to see whether the final design evoked the desired interaction qualities and incited the particular behaviors. The test was done in the Mauritshuis. Nine young adult travelers participated in the test, using a partly functional prototype while visiting the exhibition. The prototype allowed playing the game, but was limited to five treasures (instead of fifteen in the real design), and participants had to search for them in a pre-defined order. Five participants used the prototype individually and four tested it in pairs. We observed the behaviors of the nine young adult travelers while using the prototype, and asked them to share their experiences of interacting with the paintings (Figure 6). Due to the unfamiliarity of the participants to the topic, instead of asking them to answer which positive emotion they had during the session, we asked them to rate aspects of their museum experience related to the design intentions, on scales of one to five, i.e., “To which degree did you feel motivated to explore the painting?” The participants’ interactions with the apps were video-recorded for studying their actual behavior.

Based on the feedback of the young adult travelers in the evaluation session as well as our observations we

Figure 5. The interfaces of the museum app.

Figure 6. The photos of the design evaluation session.

conclude that the young adult travelers showed behaviors that were largely in line with the five design intentions:

1. Young adult travelers were encouraged to actively gain new knowledge.

The app made the participants curious to learn why a painting was different from how it was depicted in the app, and they mentioned that they were motivated to listen to the audio stories. They mentioned that the story about the local culture related to them and that it had increased their interest in understanding the paintings, as well as motivated them to see more paintings and listen to more audio fragments.

2. Social interactions between young adult travelers were triggered in the museum.

By the two pairs of participants the game of interacting with the paintings was seen as an activity that they could do together and that triggered interactions between them. They cooperated to find the paintings with the provided clues and to find the differences between the real painting and the picture in the app. The audio story about the local culture in some cases also triggered conversations between two participants, making them share previous experiences in the city.

3. Young adult travelers were motivated to explore the details of the painting.

The app incited to look for the paintings with the 'treasures' and compare the original painting with the one depicted in the app. Both activities guided them to actively look into the details of paintings. The app changed their behaviors from passively receiving the information to playing with the paintings.

4. Young adult travelers were engaged in the cozy atmosphere of the museum.

The app created an interactive museum experience without interfering with the cozy historic atmosphere in the museum. The participants appreciated the art, had fun with friends and gained new knowledge about Dutch local culture

by using the app. They appreciated that they could play and stop the app anytime they wanted.

5. Young adult travelers had a meaningful experience.

The audio stories about art and local culture and the travel tips were both created by local young adults. These were intended to imitate the experience of meeting new local friends telling them interesting stories about Dutch culture and art. The stories of the paintings and the recommendations in the travel tips from the local young adults facilitated young adult travelers to engage in the museum and in the Netherlands. It enhanced their interest to explore the city, which could make the trip more unique and meaningful

Through the evaluation of the app, we could see that the app has a potential to stimulate young adult travelers to actively learn about the paintings, interact with a companion, and open up to explore local culture even after leaving the museum. However, some usability problems were identified during the test. Prior to implementation of the concept, the flow of the user interface needs to be further refined, so that people will be able to use the app and to engage in the activities stimulated by the design without supplementary instructions.

General discussion

In this paper, we proposed a new approach in which particular positive emotions are used to influence user behavior and demonstrated its application through a design case. We first analyzed the behaviors of users in relation to their expectations and concerns, and inferred what kinds of psychological needs would underlie those. Based on the identified needs and the goal of the project, a set of positive emotions was chosen taking their associated thought-action tendencies into account, which then served as design intentions in the phase of idea generation. At the end, we evaluated the result of our design approach with the prototype of the final design.

During the design process, we encountered some challenges of clustering expectations into the needs; some expectations appeared to be difficult to relate to the exact definitions of the ten psychological needs defined by Sheldon et al. (2001). We therefore slightly

redefined the needs to fit the museum context. For example, instead of defining the competence as “one was successfully completing difficult tasks” (Sheldon et al, 2001), we transformed the definition to “one feels capable of completing the tasks one chose to perform” for clustering the expectation of gaining new knowledge about the paintings. The redefinition was based on Cognitive Evaluation Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985) indicating that people experience satisfaction if they fulfill both needs of competence and autonomy for a high level of intrinsic motivation. The broader definition of the competence helped us consider a wider range of positive emotions.

The results of the design evaluation indicated that the final design of the museum app led young adult travelers to perform the target behaviors. However, the current study comes with some limitations. Although we initially intended to see if the app could actually evoke the targeted positive emotions, the questionnaire used in the test only dealt with the possible effects of the app on the participants’ behaviors inside the museum. Measuring positive emotions at a detailed level was not possible, due to a lack of design support for that. Moreover, since the prototype was only partly functional, we could not observe the effects of the app on the participants’ behaviors after their museum visit (i.e., in terms of engaging with the local culture) and we had to rely on their self-reported opinions and intentions for that. With a more sophisticated prototype, the behavioral effects could have been examined.

Conclusion

This paper explores a new design approach based on Fogg’s (2009) claim that experiences can motivate particular behaviors. We assume that the approach provides a structure for influencing user behavior through emotions as it shows the process of conceiving favorable behaviors and positive emotions in a systematic way. Future case studies that involve different design contexts (e.g., hospitals and train stations) will allow us to further refine the proposed approach. Furthermore, in the paper we address positive emotions enhancing the motivation to perform behavioral change; however, ability and trigger, the other two factors that influence behavioral change in Fogg’s theory, could be taken into account in the future study to improve the approach.

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Avenues, values, and the muse: An ethnographic study of creative activity to support the wellbeing of residents living with dementia in residential care

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Abstract This paper presents the preliminary ethnographic stage of an ongoing PhD project that aims to explore how ludic, and creative activities can support older residents living with dementia in residential care. Observations of care units, as well as formal and informal interviews with care staff provided an understanding of the daily routines and activity within the environment, identified in-house activities, and gave insights into supporting the wellbeing of residents. Observations of arts based activity sessions, and interviews with the creative practitioners who deliver them, provided insights into how creative activities can be a valuable resource in supporting the wellbeing of residents living with dementia, as well as the limitations associated with this field. The paper presents the context for the research question and outlines the methods that were used in addressing it. A summary of the findings are given followed by a brief discussion, focusing on the value that creative activity has for a dementia care environment which is facing significant challenges. The findings are used to support future research to identify ways in which design can manifest and promote the value of creative activity within the dementia care environment.

Keywords *Dementia, Subjective wellbeing, Care environment, Creativity, Methods*

Introduction

Individuals living with dementia can face challenges in supporting their subjective wellbeing as the means to do so can be reduced through cognitive decline. For those in the care environment these issues can be exasperated as access to the physical or social avenues, previously relied upon, are limited or removed entirely (Kitwood, 1997). For older individuals participation in creative activity has been shown to support wellbeing in ways that are in accord with human flourishing (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013); such as health improvements, reduced medication use, increased levels of interest and engagement, as well as broadening social interactions (Cohen et al., 2006; Cutler, 2009). Brod et al. (1999) suggest that the domains that support wellbeing are the same in those living with dementia as those who are not. However, they conclude that the unique characteristics of the disease dramatically shape these domains, and that in order to support wellbeing in this context one needs to adopt a disease specific conceptualisation of the term in areas that "directly [relate] to cognitive, behavioural, and social changes accompanying disease progression" (ibid).

This paper describes research undertaken during the preliminary stages of an ongoing PhD project looking

at ways in which creative activities can support the subjective wellbeing of older individuals with dementia living in the care environment. An ethnographic approach was used to identify how the context of dementia shapes creative activity within this environment with the aim of applying this knowledge to new strategies. The context, approach, and methods of the project are presented and followed by a brief summary of selected findings. The subsequent discussion poses the question as to whether Experience Design (Hassenzahl et al., 2013) offers a framework for new creative strategies to support wellbeing in the dementia care environment, and a brief outline for future research is presented.

Context

Dementia is a syndrome used to describe a set of progressively degenerative symptoms associated with neurological diseases affecting the functioning of the brain, for which there is currently no cure (WHO, 2012). This year a person will be diagnosed with dementia every 3.2 seconds, equating to 9.9 million new cases (Prince et al., 2015). A recent review of statistics estimates that there are currently 46 million people living with the disease. This figure is expected to nearly double every twenty years (ibid). The prevalence of dementia increases significantly with age and

improvements in health care and quality of life have enabled a rapid growth of those aged 60 and over. Therefore, an ageing population combined with projected cases of dementia presents considerable challenges for the social, economic, and service sectors. A situation that the World Health Organization describes as “one of the major challenges for development in the twenty-first century” (WHO & Alzheimer’s Disease International, 2012).

Amongst this major challenge is a call to find ways to mitigate the pressure facing dementia care services. Current estimates indicate that global dementia care costs stand at USD \$818 billion, which is calculated to rise to USD \$2 trillion in 2030 (Prince et al., 2015). Care needs to support an elderly person with dementia are significantly more demanding than many other chronic long term illnesses (Prince et al., 2013). As symptoms progress these increasing needs mean that many of those living with the disease require professional support, often becoming residents of long term care (Train et al., 2005).

In the UK one third of individuals diagnosed with dementia are living in long term care environments. This figure means that 80% of service users in residential and nursing care are living with a form of dementia or cognitive impairment (Alzheimer’s Society, 2014). A predicted increase of service users combined with a challenging economic context means that strategies to support quality of life and wellbeing for residents will need to be efficient, resourceful, and focused.

Activities and wellbeing

Participating in activities is fundamental to the pursuit of wellbeing (Lyubomirsky, 2007), and can be regarded as intrinsic to human nature (Csikszentmihalyi, 1993). For those living with dementia activities remain fundamental avenues to supporting psychological needs (Kitwood, 1997), and can be regarded as more important to an individual’s wellbeing than their physical and social environment (Perrin, 1997). Whilst creative activities have been shown to benefit the wellbeing of residents living with dementia (Palmiero et al., 2012), studies show that activities in the care environment are only successful in supporting wellbeing if delivered in the correct context (Cohen-Mansfield et al., 2012). However, within the residential care environment time constraints, targets, and limited resources often mean that attaining to physical care needs take precedent over the psychological needs (Green & Cooper, 2000). Activities are delivered by untrained staff (College of Occupational Therapists, 1998), often in large groups to as many residents as possible. In this context activities risk becoming a ‘box ticking’ exercise, or perceived as passive entertainment rather than meaningful engagement, which can leave residents sidelined or disengaged. Activity done purely for the sake of ‘doing something’ holds little value and will fail to contribute to a sense of wellbeing (Harmer & Orrell, 2008), the essential and defining factor is that the activity should be considered meaningful by the participant. Meaningful and therefore pleasurable activity can be defined as that which successfully

allows an individual to meet and fulfill their psychological needs (Hassenzahl et al., 2013).

Therefore the research seeks to build an understanding of how creative activities can provide avenues to fulfill the psychological needs for residents, and to ask whether we can use this understanding to develop sustainable activities that are inline with the requirements of the care environment.

The project

The research presented in this study formed the preliminary stages of an ongoing PhD study aiming to identify how ludic (non goal orientated) creative activities can be used to support the subjective wellbeing of older individuals living with dementia in residential care.

The PhD project is located within the Centre for Applied Research in Inclusive Arts and Design (CARIAD), a multidisciplinary research group that uses participatory design methods to address social challenges. Amongst the group’s research portfolio are: LAUGH (Ludic Artefacts Using Gesture and Haptics), an AHRC funded international collaboration to develop innovative playful devices for people living with late stage dementia; and HANDS (Helping Assist with New Devices for Seniors), a portfolio of inclusive and participatory design research projects investigating innovative ways to increase the subjective wellbeing of people with dementia.

This project’s partner and main stakeholder are Gwalia Cyf, a leading social care provider who has granted access to a number of specialist dementia units in residential and nursing environments located in South Wales, UK.

Methodology

Designing for wellbeing undoubtedly involves understanding the subjective experience of the user (Kaufmann & Engel, 2014). However, residents in long term care are often living with mid to advanced stages of dementia, and can be experiencing severely diminished reasoning, comprehension, and even limited access to the subjective domain (Ott et al. 1996). Limiting the inclusion of those who are being designed for, based on the same limitations that one is trying to support, presents a paradox which contrasts Kitwood’s (1997) key principle to view the person and not the symptoms. Bond & Conner (2001) presents a sound argument for inclusion by suggesting that “there are no unique methodological challenges in researching dementia. Rather, the complex nature of dementia and dementia care highlight the methodological challenges of investigating complex social phenomena.” And indeed studies such as Kaufmann & Engel (2014) demonstrate the value of such inclusion by applying qualitative methods to obtain first hand data on the subjective experience of those living with late stage dementia. However, it is clear that such an approach would require considerable knowledge and experience of both the ‘complex nature of dementia,’ and of applying research tools and methods within challenging social phenomena. As both this knowledge and experience

were beyond the current range of the PhD researcher, an approach that designed *for* people with dementia rather than *with* people with dementia was chosen. In line with the literature (Brooker, 1995; Lindsay, 2012) the preliminary stages focused on gaining an understanding of the field, thus an ethnographic approach (Atkinson, 2001) using observations and interviews was applied in order to do so.

Procedures

Involvement with the CARIAD research team allowed the author to shadow qualitative interviews, observations, and pilot studies all of which were undertaken within the dementia care environment. This experience provided valuable grounding for the protocols, methods, and personal approach that is required in conducting research in sensitive and complex areas.

Initial meetings were conducted with key managerial staff members from the stakeholder, Gwalia Cyf, in order to explain the aims of the project, and as an opportunity to discuss the proposed ethnographic methods of conducting observations and interviews. The stakeholder granted the researcher an honorary working contract, which provided the same level of insurance and access as care staff whilst on site.

Following this, approval was successfully obtained from the University's Research Ethics Committee to conduct observations of dementia care units and activity groups, as well as to collect data through formal and informal interviews with care staff and activity service providers. Literature suggesting that differences in managerial approaches can influence the structure of the care units, and the variety of activities provided to residents, (Harmer & Orrell, 2008) raised the question as to whether focusing on a single care provider may impact on the generalisation of findings at later stages. Therefore the ethical approval allowed for research to be undertaken with care providers other than the project's main stakeholder.

Initial aims focused on familiarization using traditional ethnographic methods of observing and talking to those who worked in the field. Focus at this stage was on obtaining insights into the variety of creative activities that are available to residents, to explore how these were delivered, to identify the resources being used and how they were applied, and to identify activities that were deemed to be successful in supporting wellbeing and to ask why. The goal being to use this data to find patterns (Hassenzahl et al., 2013) in activities that support wellbeing, and to use these patterns as a framework for developing new strategies or activities in later stages.

Methods

Interviews

Case study interviews (Yin, 2014) were conducted with a range of individuals involved with delivering creative activities for dementia care services. The intention was to understand the term 'activities' from

as many viewpoints as possible such as front line staff, project managers, and activity providers and facilitators. Following informal agreement to take part in the study all participants were sent a project information form and consent form, both having previously been approved by the University Research Ethics Committee.

Wherever possible the interviews were conducted in person at the participant's place of work and were audibly recorded. In two instances a personal meeting was not possible and the interviews were conducted using Skype, in these cases screen-capturing software was used to make both audio and visual recordings. As the aim of this stage was to explore the field, semi-structured interviews were used in order to allow flexibility in questioning, and to peruse key points which may emerge (Silverman, 2013). The interview questions were tailored slightly to fit the participant's job and focus on their area of expertise, but the core questions remained the same throughout. These core questions focused on eliciting practical knowledge as well as opinions and experiences on the style of activity provided to residents, how activities were delivered/facilitated, how activities were tailored to specific needs/environment, how activities provide pleasure, and how activities are evaluated. Each interview lasted between 45 minutes to an hour.

Participants

Participant selection was made from a snowball approach through the course of the research stage. Interviewees included a member of Gwalia Cyf's care team, recommended by managerial staff on account of their ability to support residents using playful and meaningful activity. An activities coordinator who managed a service delivering a horticulture activity, to a broad range of dementia units, for one of South Wales' leading mental health and wellbeing charities. Also, three creative arts facilitators specializing in print making, clay sculpting, and drama therapy/clowning who had been involved in a two year project delivering creative activities within the care environment to the project's stakeholder. An expert interview was conducted with John Killick, a poet, creative practitioner/facilitator, and well cited author on dementia who's work supports the promotion of personhood for those living with the disease through methods that celebrate and advocate the creative and playful possibilities within dementia care (Killick, 2012).

Observations

In parallel to collecting interview data observations of facilitated activity sessions were conducted in a variety of residential care environments. In total five activity groups delivered by trained practitioners were observed; these included a horticulture activity, a music and movement group, two 'quiz and reminiscence' activity sessions, and an intergenerational clay-sculpting event involving local school children. Each activity session lasted between 1 and 2 hours.

In order to contextualize the data it was felt that an understanding of the daily routine within the care

environment was necessary. As such observations of four different dementia care units were undertaken on days when there was no organised activity session run by a trained practitioner. Six separate observations took place in care units, each observation session lasting for approximately four hours. The sessions took place between the hours of 8.00 am to 6.00 pm in order to view as many different aspects of the working day as possible, including medication rounds, in-house activity sessions, quiet periods, and meal times. Only the common areas of the care environment were observed such as lounges, activity rooms, and dining areas. It was the author's decision not to conduct observations through the evening or early morning as it was felt that this would be too obtrusive for both carers and residents, furthermore informal conversations had suggested that most activity takes place during the day.

For both the organised activity sessions and the daily routine observations, jot notes (Walford, 2009) were taken in situ using a discrete notepad and pencil. These notes were then reflected upon and written up in long hand once off site, either the same evening or as soon as was possible. Observational data collection focused on both the physical and social environment. Notes were taken regarding the number of residents in the room, number of staff in the room, layout of the room, types of activities that were engaged in, objects and materials used in activities, levels of engagement of staff and residents, interactions between staff and residents, accessibility and availability of activities to residents.

Analysis

Audio and visual recordings of the interviews were anonymised and transcribed verbatim. The software package NVivo 10 for Mac was used for data management. Thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) was chosen for its flexibility and accessibility to early stage researchers. As this stage was concerned with forming an understanding, rather than confirming or developing theories, an inductive approach was used to analyze the data. Patterns and themes that appeared across all interviews were valued as significant, as well as those that gave rich descriptions and specific examples.

Although only quotes taken from the qualitative interviews are cited as examples in this paper, it was the knowledge obtained from the observational studies that contributed to the active analysis of this data set and in identifying the patterns and themes that were of interest.

Findings

The findings presented are a summary of a selection of key points that address the question of how creative activities can be used to support subjective wellbeing for residents living with dementia in the care environment. This is followed by a bullet point summary, and a short discussion in which a direction for future research is presented.

Creative outcomes

In-house arts sessions appear to be a common staple

on the activity timetable within the care environment. These are often described as 'arts & craft' activities, and are run by members of care staff. The methods used are generally based on simple techniques and resources. Using themes such as seasonal events or holidays they tend to focus on producing outcomes, such as seasonal decorations, which can then be used to turn available windows, shelves, or walls into temporary exhibitions within the building. The artefacts can however appear quite crude or overtly simplistic in nature, which may lead staff to be conscious of the outcomes. When talking about a window display depicting paper cut outs of seasonal fauna a staff member involved explained,

"I didn't want to do more in case it looked like a nursery."

Kitwood stresses that the provision of meaningful activity 'requires a great deal of skill and imagination to meet the need for occupation, in a way that does not impose false solutions, crude and ready-made' (Kitwood, 1997). A deficit of activities designed specifically for this demographic (Treadaway et al., 2014) results in activities being chosen for residents that are based on the physical and mental ease with which they can be completed, leading to products that have been designed for a much younger age group being considered suitable.

Creative process

Funding requirements often stipulate that tangible outcomes, or products, are an essential goal of professionally delivered arts projects. However, for the creative practitioner, an emphasis on producing these outcomes can impact on the sessions by taking the focus away from the creative process.

"If you have to make a product you have to start... timetabling, you have to start nudging people in certain directions because you need them to do certain things."

Rather than sessions center around completing an outcome or achieving a goal the creative practitioners expressed a clear value in the positive experiences that arose through the process. In these instances it was the case that laughter, positive atmosphere, as well as 'engagement and satisfaction' were, to them, important indicators of success.

"A lot of it is just how it feels [on] every visit, if people are having a good time and... the staff are happy, and the residents are happy then you know that's successful."

"And that [residents] got into it, they had this lovely feeling of getting drawn into the material and that focusing thing, ...what do the psychologists call it? Flow."

This point is demonstrated in an account of a resident living with advanced stages of dementia and experiencing very limited communication, mobility, and hand use. Over a number of weeks the resident found meaning in the process of drawing.

"[He] liked to draw, he liked to have a pencil or a pen in his hand, and you could see him start to sort of make marks. And it was, somehow, he was guiding, you know, it was giving him something to actually focus on."

Within the context of dementia the smallest action can take on profound meaning (Snyder, 2001), here engagement in the act of mark making for a sustained period indicates a significant level of meaning. Crucially, it seems to suggest that engagement and pleasure in the process appears to be accessible to residents despite diminished cognitive functioning (Palmiero et al., 2012).

Avenues towards personhood

A shift in focus from product to process opens further opportunities in which creative activities can support personhood. Dementia can lead to the loss of an individual's ability to engage in previously valued skills through cognitive and physical decline. This loss of skill not only reduces the opportunity, or avenues, to fulfill psychological needs, but it can lead an individual to withdrawal from activities in order to avoid embarrassment or shame (Snyder, 2001).

"She loved art because she'd done it, [but] she'd also lost that, because she'd got more impaired over the years. So sometimes she'd be really depressed about how little she could do now. Staff were always like, "Oh I don't know if she'll come today." And we'd always say, "Oh invite her to come." Because she loved being in a group, she always had interesting things to say or she'd be our critic; she'd go "Oh yes that's very good." And she loved giving us advice... And we really valued that in her."

Considering the session as only a linear activity, or a set of practical steps to make an artefact or outcome, risks missing the range of opportunities that are available to support wellbeing. The data showed facilitated activities were able to provide opportunities for experiences that can lead to significant benefits for an individual with dementia (Sullivan et al., 2002), including opportunities to socialize, contribute to self identity, facilitate a sense of agency, provide meaningful purpose, and to feel valued by others.

Flexibility

The importance of flexibility was evident in the props and materials used as well as the preparation of activity. Often when entering the care environment the activity facilitator faced a range of unknown variables. Only on arrival would they know who they would be working with, how many people would be in the group, the mood of the group, whether any individuals may be experiencing distress or require additional attention. The same is true for daily care provision, fluctuating physical abilities associated with dementia (Murphy et al., 2010) means an activity that may be accessible to a resident one day may be unsuitable the next.

A flexible approach also played an important part in allowing the activity to take unexpected turns.

Moments in which residents defined the direction of the activity resulted in successful, meaningful, and surprising interactions.

"In one session I had a ball with the world printed onto it. And some people could see it was the world, the globe, and they would talk about where they've been. And for other people it was just something to squeeze like one of those stress balls. And [in] one session we just ended up blowing the ball across the table. It was great because suddenly everybody had to fill up their lungs, so that was very life affirming... And that didn't come from me, I didn't even think of that, what a brilliant idea!"

Recounting an intergenerational project run with a local school, a creative practitioner provides an account of a resident with dementia who had been very disengaged with previous activities. Choosing not to participate in the same way as the rest of the group, who were all creating clay models, two members of the group used the materials to develop their own activity.

"The one that caught my attention the most was [name excluded], the guy that could be quite, you know, he spoke quite poetically about the war. He teamed up with this very shy girl and they started playing tic-tac-toe on the clay, drawing on it and then wiping it off, taking advantage of the fact that it was such a changeable material. And they started playing this game, and they played it for ages. And they were both totally into it, just very amused you know, laughing away to each other and if anyone talked to them they'd be like, you know, 'Don't interrupt!' And get back to playing their game of tic-tac-toe on this sheet of clay. So that surprised me, I never would have thought about suggesting doing that."

The ability to make connections and come up with new possibilities is indicative of creativity. Here the term creativity should be not be restricted to outcomes or activities but instead can be considered in a broader sense. A creative mindset within this environment allows for unexpected moments to emerge, and to be turned into memorable events.

Engagement

Asking participants to engage in any creative activity will always have limitations, many of which can be attributed with associations with the word 'creative' itself (Weisberg, 1986), causing those who do not consider themselves 'creative' to take flight. However, a recurring theme within the data was the willingness of residents to take part in new creative activities.

"The average person who is functioning well will have that thing, 'Oh no!' Or maybe if they can draw they'll be, "Oh yeah I can draw." But there's an ego involved which isn't there with people with dementia, they don't, I don't think they're that self conscious."

Data showed that residents were willing to try new activities and experiences (Snyder, 2001), and that activities could become opportunities to celebrate life, to have fun, and to feel connections to others and to the self (Dupuis, et al., 2010). However, to access the

opportunities in these areas requires a sensitive ear and for the creative process to be valued.

Perception of creative activities in the care environment

The value attributed to creative activity within the care environment can be low. It is unclear whether this is because simplistic methods set the standard, whether time constraints, appropriate resources, or personal preferences of care staff play a factor. The impression that one creative practitioner had was that some staff were skeptical as to the validity or effectiveness of the sessions.

"It was like; 'These people turning up with paper and pencils and trying to get these people to draw was just ridiculous.' You could see it, them thinking that"

At times some care staff viewed the creative activity sessions in terms of passive entertainment rather than as opportunities for considered engagement, with residents being 'wheeled in' part way through an organised and carefully facilitated session and expecting them to 'pick it up.' A similar impression from another creative practitioner offers potential insight into why this opinion might be held.

"I think when we first went in, the carers were a bit like 'Oh here we go, you're just going to wind everybody up and then leave us with chaos.' Circus comes to town, you know, and there'll be residents who'll be stressed and anxious and uptight after we'd gone."

Positive wellbeing in residents leads to improvements in mood, reducing agitation and behaviours described as disruptive and negative. Once the effect of the activity sessions had resulted in benefits to the mood of the residents then the potential value of the activity was made manifest.

"The residents were in fact calmer, more likely to chat, more likely to laugh, eating better. [They] seemed much more positive in themselves and so the carers seemed to warm up quite a bit."

Interview data shows that support from care staff was crucial in facilitating an atmosphere that was conducive to creativity and freedom of expression, the care staff who 'understood' the purpose and potential benefits for residents were described as 'the glue that kept it together,' and as valuable links between facilitator and residents.

Summary of findings

- *Creative activity can support wellbeing for residents living with dementia in ways that adhere to Kitwood's model of psychological needs.*
- *Avenues to wellbeing can be increased by focusing on the creative process, and not the end product.*
- *Experiences that provide pleasure are valuable resources in this environment for both residents and care staff.*
- *Contextualizing activity through the lens of dementia is required to recognize meaning in the smallest detail.*

- *Creative activities may face barriers in terms of value within the care environment.*
- *The values associated with strategies will determine staff acceptance and therefore influence the likelihood of long-term application of these strategies.*
- *Visible benefits to the wellbeing of residents can lead to an activity being valued.*

Discussion

In researching ways that creative activities can support the wellbeing of people with dementia the data shows that avenues to support wellbeing can be identified in the outcomes, the process, and the facilitation of activity. Empathy with the process of creativity appears to contribute to an approach that recognizes, understands and values the opportunities for pleasure in the processes of engaging in arts based activities.

If diagnosis figures are correct then the demands on the dementia care sector will require solutions that maximize every available resource. Creative activities can support the subjective wellbeing of residents, and happy residents ease the pressure on care staff. Therefore a significant design challenge will be to provide ways in which creativity can be recognised as a valuable resource.

Financial constraints often mean that external activities are amongst the first expenses to be cut. For strategies to achieve an impact they need to be adopted by care staff in order to sustain long term application. Therefore a successful approach to designing strategies for wellbeing within this environment would need to understand the values that are felt to be significant to care staff.

Creativity exists within the daily care environment. It may not always adhere to an artistic definition of the term, but it is evident in the adaptive ways care staff use their social skills to support residents, in the methods they develop to understand individuals who have lost the capacity of verbal communication, and in the ways they can create an atmosphere of fun and humour amid challenges. The avenues to support personhood that creative activities provide are important and valued, but accessing these avenues through traditional arts based approach may not always be recognised.

If the term 'creative' comes with connotations and expectations, then designing for experiences (Hassenzahl et al., 2013) could offer ways of harnessing these avenues in ways that are more conducive and acceptable, by removing the focus on the act of creating and instead reframing beneficial patterns as opportunities for positive experiences.

Future direction

Future stages of the project will seek to identify a framework for creative strategies that support the opportunities for wellbeing as outlined in this study. It is intended that the future methodology will be informed and supported by the data gathered during this preliminary stage and will focus on identifying

strategies that are inline with the needs, resources, and values of the care environment.

In line with Visser et al. (2005) data collected from interviews with care staff revealed only a certain level of depth, particularly when approaching potentially sensitive subject areas. Therefore an approach using generative methods (Sanders & Stappers, 2014) will be applied in order to obtain a deeper and richer data set.

Areas of specific focus will include the following:

- *Defining what the term 'activity' means to care staff; preliminary findings suggest that the definition of 'activity' can be used by staff to refer to a broad scope of interactions with residents, ranging from one-to-one conversation to organised group events.*
- *The values that care staff feel are important in supporting the wellbeing of residents; the values that staff attach to activities/strategies appear to determine the success of implementation of the strategies, therefore identifying and promoting these values may support successful frameworks.*
- *How the daily reality of the care environment may influence opinions and feelings towards activities; it is also clear that activities/strategies must be tailored to the working routines and pressures of the environment in order to be considered accessible, practical, and meaningful.*
- *Identifying current strategies to support wellbeing; focusing on patterns that can reveal how activities/strategies are best delivered, when they can be appropriately delivered, and why they work.*
- *Identifying potential barriers to creative activity; in order to reframe patterns and develop experiences that are accessible to all.*
- *Identifying the physical and psychosocial resources available within the environment; as stated the challenges facing this environment mean that all available resources should be fully utilized.*

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Designing materials experiences through passing of time – Material driven design method applied to mycelium-based composites

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Abstract As part of a research about the relationship between time and design through the topic of materials and processes, this paper presents experimentation on a novel material. New materials are emerging through a Do-It-Yourself approach encouraged by Open source behaviors and trans-disciplinary design. These materials become representative of new values, aesthetics and dynamics, which lead to an emotional bonding with the user and the designer. The need of applying a method suitable for the design of these materials is emerging. New tools for selecting, exploring and designing materials based on experience, senses and emotion are starting to be available and applied. Mycelium-based DIY material have a strong potential and might be a perfect candidate to experiment with an experience-based method, that is the Material Driven Design method. Through this method a material experience related to the passing of time and consistent with the material qualities and characteristics was developed. Combining a novel material with a novel method might lead to development both on the material and on the method itself.

Keywords *Material-driven design, Passing of time, Mycelium-based composites, Materials experience, Trans-disciplinary design*

Introduction

The study presented here shows an experimentation process on a mycelium-based composite, through *Material Driven Design* (MDD) method, that is a method supporting designers in understanding and designing the experience that the user have with and through a certain material (Karana et. al, 2015). The aim of this study was to test the method in designing a materials experience consistent with the qualities of the material itself. The inner and peculiar features of this mycelium-based composite characterized by its spontaneity and dynamism led to develop a poetic material experience linked to passing of time, which is expressed by the emotional bonding through memories, the spontaneous growing process of the living material, the signs and traces of time and usage and the imperfect aesthetic given by its rudimentary and low tech process.

The paper describes the study through the following contents: (1) Starting with a description of the **state of the art**, an exploration of the changing context of design of materials which is characterized by emerging practices and theories around Do-It-Yourself (DIY) is performed. Open Source, trans-disciplinarity and the established approach based on emotions, senses and experience, more than on technical and functional issues are addressed as well. (2) A **mycelium-based composite** is described focusing on its potential properties and its manufacturing process. (3) The main steps of the MDD **method** are applied to

the composite in order to: understanding the material, creating the material experience vision, manifesting the material experience pattern and designing the material concept. (4) The tangible and intangible **results** are then presented in the form of findings, insights, visions and material samples. (5) In the **discussion and conclusions** a critical view is presented along with the challenges that could be undertaken, the relevance of the method tested and guidelines about the further steps.

State of the art

An overview of the design context from which our study arises is addressed. As a precondition, it is needed to state that more and more designers are showing interest in materials and deepening or discovering their role as designers of materials themselves, moving away from a product-centered approach. They operate on processes, surface treatments or on the formulation itself in order to produce material innovation. It is evident that materials enormously influence the products as a whole, because they constitute their physicality and substance.

On a par with product design, theories and practices about design of materials are changing (Karana et al., 2016). This dynamic context is characterized by several intertwined factors: the established interest in the intangible characteristics of design – sensoriality, meaning, experience, among others – which led to the

development of new tools and methods for materials selection, exploration and design (Pedgley, 2014; Akın & Pedgley, 2016); the emergence of a new aesthetic related to imperfection and aging (Rognoli & Karana, 2014; Saito, 2010); the growth of transdisciplinarity in design (Brown, 2009; Aldersey et. al, 2008); the diffusion of new way to look and develop materials from a design point of view that brought to the tuning of a new class of materials, as Do-It-Yourself Materials (DIY-M) (Rognoli et al., 2015).

In fact, as described in detail by scholars (Rognoli et. al, 2015) the democratization of technological practices is bringing to an easier accessibility to technologies both owned, through cheap and flexible tools, and shared, through the notion of open source. The concept and practices of open source are manifesting in the context of materials for design through databases, physical and digital material libraries, tools for selection and inspiration, digital platforms like forums where the users, both professionals and non-professionals, are able to find information on materials and manufacturing process, even update, add materials, information and opinions, and ultimately share their experience. Producers also support open source by publishing on the Internet the recipes of their materials, like the growing materials by Ecovative Design ("Ecovative's Myco Make instructions", n.d.) and by Suzanne Lee (Lee, n.d.). Open source it is becoming more evident through Fablabs, factories and workshops for prototyping and experimentation. For sure, the diffusion of open source philosophy gets stronger the possibility for the designers to access to data related to different fields and disciplines, meet professionals with different background and start collaborations. Thus a trans-disciplinary approach in design becomes more and more diffused. From natural sciences, through design, culinary arts arriving into medicine, it is visible to our eyes how the most distant fields are starting to encounter synergy to work together. This is the case of DIYBio Labs ("DIYbio Labs homepage", 2008) where designers and scientists, namely DIY biologist, can meet and collaborate on shared project. Through cross-pollination of knowledge, practices, methods, technologies, formal languages and inspirations designers are discovering alternatives to conventions both technically and aesthetically to propose new solutions that are innovative, original, competitive, affordable and sustainable that can overtake conventional solutions provided by industries and mass production (Aldersey-Williams et al., 2008).

The growth of trans-disciplinary collaborations, combined with the democratization of technologies (Tannenbaum et al, 2013) and the diffusion of fablabs, are empowering designers to gain independence from industries. Designers are being able to self-produce materials, tools and artifacts. They can satisfy their needs of autonomy, personalization and appropriation to better express their design idea, contributing to create a different emotional relationship between artifacts and users. Materials that are self-produced by designers can be called Do-It-Yourself materials (DIY-M) (Rognoli et al., 2015). DIY Materials elicit new aesthetics and new dynamics. Usually they are

produced with local resources, promoting sustainability, reducing the costs and bringing out an emotional bonding through memories. They are characterized by the aesthetic of imperfection, which makes the material more human and emotionally connected to the user. Because they are self-made, the designer establish a personal connection with his or her creations. Through a "hands-on" approach (Nimkulrat, 2012) the designer is learning by doing and collecting experience and a know-how about that material; the user perceives the value of something self-made like it happens for handcraft. They are shared and open source allowing perpetual updates, improvements and developments made by others, generating also variations. According to Kuznetsov & Paulos (2010), any modification or repair action without the aid of paid professionals is considered a DIY practice. Moreover these practices are usually led by experimental, and sometimes artistic, impulses. Therefore, in order to produce applicable, acceptable and durable results they need to be guided by a structured design method. They are also experimental and uncompleted proposals, so their properties, limits and possibilities should be observed and understood through a method, in order to make further developments. In addition, a method is needed because another crucial point is that these materials are new, unknown and without an identity. One can state that "people can't recognize and understand the materials, because they don't have previous experience with them".

This novel class of materials transversely embraces a new design aesthetic characterized by imperfection and the passing of time (Rognoli & Karana, 2014). Designers are showing more and more interests in the effect of time and usage on artifacts, materials and processes (Annicchiaricco & Van Der Rossem, 2012). They are considering the values and experiences given by inevitable and natural aging and, as modern alchemist, they are experimenting with ingredients and solutions in order to accelerate aging and enhance the marks of time and use (Ostuzzi et al., 2011).

New tools and methods for material selection are being developed by scholars in the last 15 years (Pedgley, 2014). More than technical properties they are based on sensorial appreciation, meanings, emotion, experience and identity. In a few words, what Karana and colleagues called before *Intangible characteristic of materials* or ICM (Karana et al., 2007; Karana et al., 2010) and now call *intangible sparks* (Karana et al., 2015 a). In addition to these tools a novel method for material exploration and design focusing on Material experience and combining practical experimentation, user studies and meta-design vision was recently introduced, namely the Material-Driven Design method (MDD) (Karana et al., 2015 b). Connected to the idea of Product Experience (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007) the concept of Material experience by Karana is a key factor: "Material experience is the experience that people have through and with materials" (Karana, 2009), considering senses, meanings, emotions (Karana, 2009) and performing (Giaccardi and Karana, 2015). The user involvement and a hands-on approach required in the MDD appear

to be crucial in the understanding and experimentation with new materials in order to make them meaningful.

Taking into account this changing context, it was decided to focus on Mycelium based composite as a material that represent the best candidate to experiment with in order to understand it and develop a meaningful experience connected to passing of time and based on its characteristics and qualities. Mycelium based composite is characterized by an open source and DIY approach, together with an aesthetic process related to trans-disciplinarity, to passing of time and imperfection. The use of this natural material in everyday life was firstly promoted by the american mycologist Paul Stamets in his book *Mycelium Running: how mycelium can save the world?* (2005) and supported by a huge community as we can note from websites and dedicated pages on diy ("DIY page: Make a mycelium starter", n.d), Ukfungusday ("Ukfungusday homepage", n.d.), fungi expert David Moore website (2011), and others.

The relevance of this material is revealed by the interests shown by design education and research which are running research projects and didactic activities focused on it.

Mycelium-based composite

The aim of the research and the design context described so far was focused on this specific material. Herewith is presented the description of this DIY bio-composite material based on mycelium – *namely the roots of fungus* – and natural substrate derived from agricultural waste. It is characterized by a low tech and slow process, which is respectful of natural rhythm of growing. As a matter of fact, the process is actually the growing of mycelium through and over the fibers of the natural substrate, inside a mould, in several days (depending on the environment). After baking, the material is stabilized and inert since the mycelium is dried and dead. As a result, a compact, lightweight and insulating material arise. The main feature addressed is sustainability: entirely natural, derived from byproducts, compostable and Cradle To Cradle (Braungart & Mc. Donough, 2002).

Although the material and the process have been present in nature, during the last seven years it has been adopted and developed as design and construction material by the American company Ecovative Design ("Ecovative Design's homepage", n.d.). Other companies and designers from all over the world are showing interest in the material and are studying it and experimenting on it according to open source and DIY logics. Currently is commercially applied in packaging, furniture and insulation for architecture, whereas the experimental practices are focusing on small objects and accessories like vases, lamps, shoes, mat, ecc. One interesting application from Ecovative Design is as surf-boards and buoys.

The use of this substance as a material is novel, relatively unknown and its identity is not already defined and solid. Companies and designer that provide it or support it didn't develop a ultimate

version of it and have not already a deep understanding and knowledge of its properties, limits, constraints, and potentiality.

In general it seems a material with a high potential and suitable to be studied, to experiment with, and to develop further applying a method. Being open source, DIY and low-tech, it allows to examine easily and directly the process and to interact with it.

The process began from the Grow-It-Yourself (or Myco Make) kits sold by Ecovative Design (Ecovative Design's GIY kit, n.d.). They consist in plastic bag inside which mycelium is already inserted through the natural substrate, then dehydrated, and ready to be re-hydrated with flour and water. This choice is motivated by the necessity of restricting time and failure risks and to being supported by the assistance provided by the company.

Method

Starting from this formulation the MDD method (Karana, et al, 2015) was followed in order to understand the material and its process and to define a new vision from which design a meaningful material experience and define new development directions. The research presented was developed in several steps according to the method.

Step 1. Understanding the material

The first step of the process is related to the study of the material and is made of three simultaneous activities: tinkering with the material; user studies; material benchmark studies.

Step 1.1. Tinkering with the material

Through this step characterized by a hands-on approach it is possible to obtain information about the material's properties and how it can be processed and shaped. Furthermore the designer can have an experience of the material in first person. This step is crucial when technical data sheets are not available or are not completed, e.g. for experimental or semi-developed materials. We tested the material through (1) tinkering of the material during the process and (2) tinkering of the material after the process.

The first practice aims to deeply understand the manufacturing process of the material and comprehend the relationship between the variables of the process and certain technical and expressive-sensorial features of the processed material. Throughout four months, the process was performed six times with a pace of 2-3 weeks, producing more than 130 samples with different qualities starting from 15 kits. Each time several changes were introduced during the process as follows: including other materials; adding new ingredients; using molds of different shapes and sizes; applying textures and colors; changing the room temperature while growing; varying the duration of the process; reducing the length of the natural fibers; controlling the temperature and duration of baking. To all these variables, the unrestrained ones such as the environmental, must be considered as they often led to unexpected results: moisture; temperature and

Figure 1-6. Activities and tests of the tinkering with the material phase.

weather condition of the location in which the material grows – including diverse geographical areas – could affect the results.

The second practice aims to understand the possible surface treatments as well as to identify the resistance of the material. Different interventions were performed on the processed samples: dyeing, texturization, tests for fire resistance, water resistance, uv resistance, weather resistance, scratch resistance, tensile strength, ecc.

Material tinkering revealed to be a perpetual activity from the beginning to the end of the process, i.e. from the first attempts to the final samples.

Step 1.2. User studies

At this stage the material was introduced to groups of people, that could be addressed as possible users of it or of any artifact produced with the material – or perhaps the self-producers of the material. This step aims to describe the experiential characterization of the material.

The information was obtained through three different activities:

1. Individual interviews took place between September and November 2015.
2. Structured workshop with different activities (questionnaires, group interviews and discussions, creative activities and brainstorming sessions) with 34 students from the first year of Product Design for Innovation Master Course at Politecnico di Milano on 14th and 16th October, 2015.
3. Structured workshop with different activities (questionnaires, creative activities, practical workshop of material production, informative and educational activities) with unselected users during the third anniversary of *Coltivando*, the

convivial urban farming garden at Politecnico di Milano, on 17th October, 2015.

The questionnaire was developed in the form of a 8 pages booklet structured as a “sensorial journey” or “sensorial exploration”. To each user or group of users a sample of material was given to examine with a sequential method: sight, touch, smell, the perception of taste through smell and sound. Through this gradual exploration the user was asked to isolate each sense from the others. During sight examination a request to describe the expectation of tactile, smell, taste and sound characteristics was made in order to highlight accordance and discordance through sight expectations and real perceptions, since it was a relatively unknown material. Three more sections were added: technical properties, lifecycle, conclusion.

In order to obtain quantitative information, the Meaning Driven Material Selection (MDMS) Tool (Karana, 2009) was chosen to answer different sensorial scale ratings. With such tool, the user is able to indicate how the material is perceived in a range of seven values between two different characteristics, (e.g. soft and hard). Following Mariet Sauerwein (Sauerwein, 2015) a contribution to the tool was inserted by adding sound, smell and taste characteristic charts, senses relevance and pleasantness chart and properties charts. It is important to underline that for such selection of the characteristics to add in the charts, the main reference was the Expressive-Sensorial Atlas (Rognoli, 2004; Rognoli, 2010).

Qualitative data was collected by adding open questions in each section of the questionnaire. During the so called “sensorial journey” it was possible to investigate about the material experience throughout the four experiential levels: sensorial, emotional, interpretative, performative. For each sense the user

Figure 7-12. Images from the workshops.

was asked around sensorial perception. Activities around meanings, opinions, reactions and behaviors completed the step.

Step 1.3. Benchmark studies

A comparative analysis between the material and other materials that might be alternatives of it was performed, in order to highlight differences and similarities, weaknesses, strong points and opportunities. For the comparison three categories of materials were selected: (1) mycelium-based materials produced by companies, on the market or on development with announced commercialization; (2) concepts and experimentations of mycelium-based material made by designers and students; (3) other produced materials that have some similarities with the material and can be substitutes of it. As a tool, we used tables in which we compare the materials by their characteristics, properties, applications and values.

Step 2. Creating the material experience vision

This step aims to support the designer in summarizing the results of the previous one by putting them in relations in a coherent whole in order to bring about relevant and critical issues and to define a unique and meaningful vision. As suggested in *MDD* method, some techniques from Vision in Design *ViP* method (Hekkert & van Dijk 2011) were considered: sequentially, clusterization of data, organization of a perceptual map naming axes with opposite values and defining four direction areas. Contrasting the method, the competitors identified in the benchmarking were mapped as well according to their vision and values. That helps to understand strategic blank spaces, i.e. opportunity areas, and consequently to define a vision statement.

Step 3. Manifesting the material experience pattern

At this stage the pattern of formal qualities was defined, like the technical and expressive-sensorial characteristics to emphasize or even transfer to the material in order to make it consistent with the vision. To achieve that goal, two meanings consistent with the vision through a semantic research utilizing mind maps as a support tool were identified.

Once the meanings were defined the necessity to identify the pattern of formal qualities linked to the meanings and through them to the vision became the next step. As suggested in *MDD* we involved the user once again through *MDMS* Tool to assure an authentic pattern.

Having the opportunity sometimes to interact directly with interviewed people in their home environment it was possible to ask them to show us physical objects instead of pictures allowing us to observe the interactions between people and the selected objects in terms of emotions and performances.

The interviews were asked for both meanings. The results were organized and visualized through the modality described in the *MDMS* Tool, i.e. a chart of values and a collection of images. To visualize and to organize the information we used also another tool by Elvin Karana, the Meanings of Materials (*MoM*) Tool. In this way we could summarize the information into different categories and subcategories, i.e. meanings, users (age, gender, nationality, fields), materials (technical properties and sensorial properties), product (manufacturing process, finishes, function, shape). We also add to the framework the category interaction (performative interaction, emotional interaction). In the sub-category sensorial properties we added a colour palette, since colour revealed to be a key factor in the perception of the material and to

have a strong connection with the meaning. We added finishes (surface treatments) as a subcategory of product.

Step 4. Designing the material concept

At this stage the identified pattern was applied to the material in order to make it consistent with the vision. To do that the experience obtained from the tinkering was considered as well. Thanks to the experience obtained from tinkering, a set of samples as concepts of further developed material were produced.

Results

Several amount of findings emerged through all the method, in particular from the first step, e.g. “understanding the material”. We obtained hundreds of data on the material properties, process and perception. Through the production of more than 130 samples and the application of different treatments on them, key issues like the material properties and final appearance vary with time. Those changes are conditioned depending on the time of the process, to the environment where the process takes place (temperature, moisture, aeration), the moulding techniques (pressure, mould’s size, breathability), the the components (fibers length, fibers colour), and the interaction with other materials. Different ways of interacting with the material and different climate and geographical conditions can lead to very different results. Because mycelium is a living and spontaneous material is difficult to completely control the process even in a laboratory or with an industrial or computerized process. Imperfection and irregularity are the main features of the material. The components confer a fibrous, amorphous, irregular and uneven appearance. Areas with different degrees of softness and roughness coexist in a small portion of surface according to the distribution of mycelium and fibers. Furthermore on the material the marks of the manufacturing process become always visible: moulding parting lines, flashing and burn marks. Through user studies it was possible to understand that people generally didn’t know the material but recognized it as made by two different components. They easily recognized the “brown part” as “natural fibers, sawdust, wood chips, dried plants, branches, hay or hemp” while the “white part” was not recognized as fungus and was pointed as made of natural or synthetic foam. Thus is not completely recognizable as biodegradable, compostable, and made from by-products, and consequently the grade of sustainability by being natural. Nevertheless they addressed as “natural” and “ecological”, and as “simple”, “modest”, “affordable”, “hand-craft” and “imperfect”. From their explanations it is due to its imperfect, fibrous and inaccurate aesthetic. The analogy with a rustic and country context is diffused because of its appearance and smell which reminds hay. Through this association the material recalls positive and nostalgic feelings that link the user to modest, genuine and childhood reality. Some of the interviews linked it to traditional or old materials diffused in their material culture. A peculiar analogy with food was identified because of its colors, roughness, irregularity and burning process that make it similar to “white chocolate, homemade bread and cheese”.

Figure 13. The structure where the material samples were placed to grow.

From the benchmark studies became clear that the companies that produce and sell the material – i.e. Ecovative Design and Mycoworks – underline the value of sustainability and of performances. They often try to hide its natural appearance making it most similar as possible to other materials and using lamination, giving it the idea of sustainable surrogate of polystyrene, cork, wood, ecc. It is visible that in a controlled environment and with an industrial process the material appears more homogeneous and performing. On the contrary, concept and experimentation from designers and students working with a DIY process, materials appear similar to the samples we produced showing the same levels of imperfection and irregularity. They push the vision to other values like the poetry of the process - e.g. *Officina Corpuscoli*, attempts of luxury identity - e.g. *Mycelial forms* (Hein, n.d), the therapeutic properties of fungus - e.g. *Vivorium* (Schachtschneider, n.d.), the spontaneity of the material - e.g. *Myx*. Comparing the material with other substitutes (i.e. expanded polystyrene, expanded polyethylene, chipboard, cork, natural beton, plasterboard, edimare, pumice), it is characterized by irregularity, unprocessed appearance, sustainability and the natural and slow process.

With the techniques and tools described in the method, all this data led to a vision statement based on an emotional bonding caused by memories between user and the material: “I want that the user is involved in an authentic bonding with the material because it is recognized as matter of time and of memories, filled with history and experience, like an artifact modeled by an artisan and subject to the marks of time”.

Through the meanings “genuine” and “spontaneous”, using the tools and the techniques described in the process, a material experience pattern was defined: irregular and fibrous texture; matt, opaque and not reflective surfaces; neutral and earthy colors through natural dyeing; marks of the process and of time, inclusions of other natural materials; possibility to process the material modeling it manually, without molds; rounded, enveloping and rounded shapes.

Figure 14-15. The final samples.

Figure 16. Textures applications.

Figure 17-18. Seeds inclusions give an expressive characterization to the samples.

Figure 19-20. Seeds released gel that allows to shape the material like clay.

Figure 21-22. Linum seeds germinate enhancing the "spontaneous" meaning.

Using the pattern as inspirational hints and design guidelines, a set of final samples consistent with the vision were developed operating through rough textures, natural dyeing, inclusion of natural and irregular materials. In particular the inclusion of psyllium, chia and linum seeds brought a functional and expressive contribution. These seeds release a gel that allows to shape the material without the use of moulds, similarly to clay and make it more resistant. The tactual and visual richness of the material is increased: without the use of a mould mycelium is able to grow more making the material more velvety and softer; seeds create a genuine visual pattern on the surface. Surprisingly linum seeds germinate during the process, reinforcing the "spontaneous" meaning.

Discussion

At this stage it is clear that the material is interesting because of its unique qualities, properties, possible applications and sustainable features. In addition the method applied allowed us to develop a unique and original vision in order to elicit a meaningful material experience for the user, valorizing the concept of passing of time. The first three steps of the method were fully applied while the last one was addressed

partially, without the development of a product concept. It became clear thus, that the first three steps are well described and structured and can be performed producing excellent outcomes which fully met our goals and expectations, whereas the last one requires a more solid structure in terms of guidelines and activities.

Following MDD method the next step should be the identification of meaningful and innovative areas of application consistent with the vision. Some ideas of application and concepts have already emerged from the first step (creative activities about applications) and in the third steps (product category). We had a set of information about application in forms of sketches and descriptions (step 1), images and processed data (step 3). Anyway we suggest that a workshop activity could be organized where the participants are given the final samples and are asked to describe, sketch or design some concept ideas consistent to the meanings or to the vision. They might be helped also giving them the data and images coming from the third step. After that we should select the most promising concept and develop some prototypes.

Different challenges and critical issues are in front of

us if we want to make further development. The first challenge is about the validation of the success of the samples development according to the vision. It is necessary to understand whether the users perceive the new material identity, whether their material experience has changed, whether the features on which we focused are strengthened. This may be validated through further user-studies in the form of workshops, interviews, questionnaires and surveys. All these new data should be compared with the data from the previous user studies.

The second one is related to the acceptance of the material by the market. It may seem not suitable for the large-market logics as a consumer good because of its aesthetic, imperfection, imprecision, fragility, instability, variability. This is why we imagine it produced in a semi-handcrafting dimension.

Another challenge is validating the applications that involve contact with the human body, contact with food and kitchen contextualization both from a psychological and biological perspective: mycophobia is a diffused psychological condition, as well mushroom allergy; the possibility of substances transfer from mycelium and other organic bodies should be tested. Developing prototypes, placing them in a context and conducting further user-studies might clarify the psychological issues, whereas biological tests might answer to the biological ones.

Speaking about the tools and the method, we started from a method on progress and we adapt it to our necessity. We also added tools, modified some others, for instance in the MoM tool by introducing new categories and subcategories, and we deepen some steps like the user studies.

Now that we learnt how to do it, next step is starting from the basis of the material choosing the ingredients from local resources and not the diy kit from a company.

Conclusions

The study presented here shows an experimentation process on a mycelium-based composite. The goal set at the beginning of the study was firmly achieved. Namely, understanding the material and developing an experience that enhance its qualities and characteristics related to the passing of time, adding value to the material, making it meaningful and opening new development directions. Eventually the results revealed to be consistent with the expectations. Furthermore, tinkering with a novel material brought to unexpected and inspiring results. As a result of the process, a novel and meaningful use of mycelium-based composites were identified, by emphasizing its spontaneous, imperfect and uncontrollable characteristics and by avoiding to strive for the adoption of a standard and industrial identity.

As presented, the improvement around the sensibility to understand the materials was evident focusing particularly on sensorial qualities. This was possible thanks to direct tinkering on materials. Indeed a "hands-on" approach proved to be crucial and

inextricable in the understanding of the material and of *what the material does* (Karana et. al., 2015 b).

It was an iterative journey of trial and error in which we learnt from both successes and failure. Through this practice experience and familiarity in dealing with the material and a *know-how* of the process was acquired. This know-how is even valuable considering that the material is novel, experimental and has promising properties, applications and sustainable features.

Another crucial issue was the user integration at different stage of the design process, from the understanding of the material to the concepts development. Through this kind of collaborative design it was possible to apply and improve some user-studies techniques and to build them up with a material-based approach.

Furthermore the learning of methods and tools by their application was a key point of the process and for our own training and improvement.

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Appendix 1. User studies - Questionnaire

Appendix 2. User studies - data charts

Appendix 3. User studies - Persona tool

ALESSANDRO
IL DIFFIDENTE
27 ANNI
GRAFICO

<<Questo materiale alla vista mi perprime. Non mi piace perché è molto irregolare, sembra rovinato. Sembra una buccia d'arancia. Mi disgusta perché sembra anche un formaggio. Concettualmente mi dà un'idea di sporcizia e di disordine, anche se naturale in un certo senso. Anche se non sono sicuro che sia completamente naturale. Sembra fatto di gesso, oppure stucco, oppure con una schiuma sintetica. Sembra artificiale, ma che vuole imitare il naturale. Non apprezco la sua superficie perché non di qualità. Insomma, si capisce che è meno raffinato di altri materiali, che non è di qualità, che è poco durevole. Io in casa mia non lo vorrei mai. Anche perché sembra molto fragile: sembra che si graffi e si rovini solamente a guardarlo. Secondo me per poter essere utilizzato deve essere ricoperto da altri materiali. Non deve essere mostrato. Oppure deve essere utilizzato come materiale secondario o usa e getta. Anche perché a vederlo non sembra avere particolari capacità meccaniche, né a trazione, né a compressione. Ma proviamo a toccarlo: beh, le mie idee sono confermate. Anche se è più resistente di come me lo immaginavo sono ancora molto critico. Non lo trovo piacevole a causa della sua irregolarità e fragilità superficiale. All'olfatto l'odore è acido e disgustoso: sento una nota principale di cantina umida, cassette di legno, stalla>>

SERENA
L'ENTUSIASTA
42 ANNI
EDUCATRICE

<<Appena ho visto il materiale mia ha dato un'idea di calore, accoglienza e calma: mi rimanda ad ambienti incontaminati e rurali, a una campagna senza la tecnologia. Questa cosa mi tranquillizza e mi dà un senso di calma. E si vede che tutela l'ambiente perché chiaramente è naturale, anche se non capisco di cosa è fatto. Sono sicura di potermi fidare. Questa idea di bucolico mi rimanda a un significato romantico del materiale. Ah, un'altra cosa è che mi ricorda qualcosa da mangiare, un torrone, una meringa o del cioccolato bianco. Già alla vista mi ispira molte emozioni positive e sono molto curiosa di toccarlo. Al tatto la mano scivola in modo piacevole sulla superficie. Ha un lato molto soffice. È un'emozione calma di gioco, relax perché leggero e morbido. Dici che la morbidezza è la sua qualità caratterizzante. Al tatto mi dà un'idea di riposo, rilassatezza, protezione, sicurezza e familiarità. Sembra a tratti anche una pagnotta: mi dà un'idea di casa, infanzia, dolcezza. Mi piace perché è morbido e leggero, non pericoloso, mi rimanda al gioco e all'infanzia: vorrei sdraiarmi sopra, come su un materassino per lo yoga, o camminarci sopra, per sentire i piedi che affondano. È bello perché ha delle parti lisce e altre ruvide: divertenti! All'olfatto è veramente buono: me lo mangerei! All'aspetto mi piace perché mi fa sentire protetto. Mi piacerebbe molto usarlo>>

EMILIO
L'INTERESSATO
34 ANNI
ARTISTA

<<Che materiale interessante e inusuale! Direi che è un composto naturale e sostenibile di quelli che realizzano ora, come quello a base di canapa. La sua identità naturale non è celata: i materiali che lo compongono gli danno un aspetto graziosamente umile. È molto onesto in questo: fa vedere i materiali che lo compongono. Credo che l'aspetto costituisca la sua stessa estetica: economico, leggero e immediato. Al tatto è molto ricco. Ricorda qualcosa di nocciolo, o qualcosa di molto antico, per la sua ruvidità. Ma non è solo ruvido. È anche morbido. Che aspetto interessante! Non sembra avere proprietà tecniche innovative, ma nelle sue semplicità è interessante. Mi sembra semplice ma rielaborato in modo innovativo senza però diventare o voler sembrare ultra-tecnologico. Ricorda un ritorno "primitivo" ai materiali semplici che non necessitano di ricerche esorbitanti sulla reperibilità. È evidente la sua natura sperimentale, ed è bello che ci si stia muovendo in questa direzione. È un materiale che vedrei bene nel futuro che vorrei io. Richiama anche il mondo dell'artigianato e del DIY. Racconta, nella sua umiltà e nel suo essere democratico, una storia legata all'artigianato. Il tempo del processo, secondo me, giustifica il costo. Ma questo materiale non sa raccontarsi completamente. Si può intervenire: la geo-caratterizzazione può essere molto rilevante>>

ROBERTA
LA CONFUSA
23 ANNI
STUDENTESSA

<<È un materiale strano. Alla vista mi incuriosisce, ma allo stesso tempo mi disgusta. Credo che sia relativamente pesante, molto duro e rigido, molto ruvido. La sua immagine mi ispira dei sentimenti un po' piacevoli: credo che anche all'odore non sia piacevole. Ma nel momento in cui lo tocco il materiale mi sorprende molto. Alla vista pensavo che fosse molto pesante e corposo. Al contrario è leggerissimo e mi trasmette piacere. Da una sensazione di vuoto interno. Inoltre mi aspettavo non fosse per niente flessibile. Mi ha sorpreso per la sua flessibilità. Alla vista sembrava più fragile e poroso. Invece ora mi colpisce per la sua compattezza e solidità. La superficie è piana e più liscia e morbida di come immaginavo. Anzi la immaginavo proprio al contrario. Invece è molto bello perché liscio e leggero. Alla vista sembra più friabile di come è. Pensavo che avesse un odore intenso e sgradevole probabilmente come l'uovo. Invece sa di menta e sigarette. Nonostante mi abbia colpito, non sono sicura che mi piaccia, e credo che ci siano ancora molte cose da sviluppare. È evidente la sua natura sperimentale. Deve essere migliorato, ma è interessante e ambizioso. Non è un materiale che apprezco come materiale da usare, è interessante solo da studiare>>

Appendix 4. Benchmark studies - Comparative charts

CHARACTERISTICS	irregularity	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	fibrosity	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	roughness	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	softness	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	insulation	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	resistance	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	weight	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	flexibility	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	building	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	packaging	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
APPLICATIONS	water related	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	furniture	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	product	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	body-related	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
	values	//	surrugate sustainability versatility / DIY education	surrugate sustainability	surrugate sustainability	surrugate sustainability	surrugate sustainability	surrugate sustainability	surrugate sustainability

Appendix 5. Vision - Clusterization

CONTATTO CON IL CORPO

Porta l'utente a toccarlo, tastarlo, grazie alla sua piacevole morbidezza. Molti utenti vorrebbero coltivare i materiali organici, e lo vedrebbero bene per realizzare materassi o solette di scarpe. Vivorium è un concept di solette di scarpe in questo materiale. Ecovative sta realizzando un materiale adatto a materassi.

Viene percepito come un materiale caldo, accogliente, tranquillizzante, innocuo e sano. È un materiale non aggressivo, ma protettivo, alla vista, al tatto e all'udito.

I funghi sono terapeutici e utilizzati in diversi farmaci medici. Il profumo del materiale può ricordare una pianta medicinale cinese.

UN MATERIALE SECONDARIO

Già viene attribuita una natura molto funzionale, perché isolante e leggero.

Alcuni utenti non lo considerano abbastanza interessante esteticamente per applicazioni primarie. Viene considerato un materiale di servizio.

Secondo alcuni intervistati è troppo fragile, anche esteticamente, perché possa essere utilizzato senza essere rivestito. Alcuni utenti non sono così propensi a toccarlo per questo motivo.

Rimangono impressi su di esso i segni di chi lo tocca, i graffi. È piuttosto semplice rimuovere alcune fibre in superficie, sfregandolo. Si sponca piuttosto facilmente.

Molte aziende lo usano per le sue proprietà funzionali ma rassicurandolo. Il materiale viene anche servito, serve ad altri oggetti e a proteggere altri cose. Ecovative e Mycoworks lo usano nei packaging e edilizia.

Non ha ancora un'identità abbastanza forte e applicazioni significative per potergli dare una certa dignità.

ETICO ED EDUCATIVO

Se il fungo è commestibile, il materiale può essere portato fino alla crescita del fungo per frange nutrimento (Dermoflora, Back to the Roots, Siamets). Questo può aiutare a soddisfare il bisogno di cibo mondiale, specialmente in situazioni di emergenza.

Il fungo facilita il degrafo di materiale, e può essere applicato nella dissimulazione di materiali tossici, come la plastica, o nella dissimulazione di sostanze organiche (Officina Corpuscoli).

Ha un ciclo di vita sostenibile, secondo il modello cradle-to-cradle. Ecovative dispone di un kit educativo.

Deriva da scarti. Il costo è basso e risolve il problema della dissimulazione di materiale di scarto e un materiale democratico.

Le persone devono essere educate a un comportamento più sostenibile e devono essere informate su metodi alternativi e più sostenibili per produrre cibo, materiali e per la dissimulazione di sostanze.

Gli utenti percepiscono la necessità per il materiale di comunicare questi valori anche a scopo educativo.

NOSTALGICO E TRADIZIONALE

La base del materiale è un substrato di scarti agricoli. Il processo del materiale è quello della crescita.

L'utente gli attribuisce dei significati di nativo, contadino, campese, campagnolo, naturale ecc. e lo immagina in esportazioni all'aperto, nell'aria, o in contesti rurali.

Viene ricordato i materiali tradizionali, utilizzati nel passato per costruire abitazioni.

Sembra un materiale piuttosto primitivo, rozza, proveniente da un altro tempo, ma anche piuttosto semplice, persino, anche «non ricorda un materiale che potrebbe essere modellato dai nativi» dice un ragazzo.

Importanza emergente del tempo contemporaneo, tipico di altre epoche.

La sensorialità, in particolare l'olfatto porta a rievocare ricordi. Il materiale viene considerato nostalgico perché porta a ricordare delle esperienze.

Il materiale ha una componente olfattiva molto rilevante che lo ricorda paragoni composti: funghi, odori del legno, del tabacco, odori familiari. Secondo alcuni fa ricordare l'infanzia, e viene trovato rassicurante.

Attraverso la memoria le persone stabiliscono un legame affettivo con l'olfatto che porta alla sua durata.

MANUALITÀ, ARTIGIANATO E DIY

Il processo del materiale può essere DIY, ma non viene sottolineato molto questa dimensione da parte dei produttori. Il materiale comincia poco questa sua qualità e questa poesia del processo.

Il suo processo senza tecnologia e con processi e strumentazioni semplici fa emergere i segni del processo sulla sua superficie.

Il materiali diventa personale, secondo le tecniche e l'esperienza dell'utente, secondo l'ambiente in cui cresce e secondo le risorse di partenza. La personalizzazione secondo l'area geografica viene considerata dagli utenti come una caratteristica piacevole.

Comportamento crescente dell'auto-produzione di materiali per avere autonomia, accelerare i tempi. Inoltre, tramite i materiali DIY si instaura un legame più profondo con il materiale. Un processo lento, tradizionale e manuale viene percepito come intriso di valori, storia, esperienza e memoria.

SPONTANITÀ E DINAMISMO

Il materiale cresce in modo autonomo e non è possibile controllarlo. È un materiale vivo.

Il risultato finale varia secondo l'ambiente, l'attrezzatura, le tecniche ed esperienza dell'utente e le risorse di partenza.

La superficie difficilmente risulta levigata. Mostra i segni dell'imperfezione che derivano dalla natura viva del materiale.

C'è il rischio che si sviluppino delle muffe se contaminato o se non cotto abbastanza.

Esiste ed è stata resistita negli utenti la micofobia: reazione nei confronti dei funghi, o credere che possa essere dannoso.

LEGAME CON LA CUCINA

Il materiale ricorda il cibo per la sua imperfezione superficiale, per il suo colore bianco-beige, per la sua superficie vellutata e texturizzata, per il suo odore, e per i segni della cottura.

Il processo del materiale è associabile alla cucina in alcune parti. Secondo alcuni utenti anche gli ingredienti derivano dal cibo, ad esempio latte e frumento.

Viene individuato un legame con un'alimentazione integrale, sana, tradizionale e genuina.

L'associazione con il cibo può essere piacevole o disgustosa a seconda della persona. Per alcuni può essere confortevole e rassicurante.

NOVITÀ E SORPRESA

Il materiale è nuovo per tutti gli utenti e risulta innovativo.

Non si conoscono le proprietà: toccarlo e annusarlo porta a sorprese tattili e olfattive: la vista suggeriva altro.

Quando viene rivelato l'ingrediente micelio e il processo di crescita la persona sono positivamente colpite e piacevolmente stupite.

La scoperta della ricchezza tattile del materiale genera piacere.

Secondo molte persone questo materiale è necessario, ma viene anche percepito come materiale non ancora pronto o finito, in corso di sperimentazione.

Il problema dell'identità di un nuovo materiale è reale: alcuni designer stanno facendo sperimentazioni con il colore e inclusioni per potergli dare nuovi significati e nuove identità.

Appendix 6. Vision - Map

Appendix 7. Pattern - semantic map

Appendix 8. Pattern - MDMS tool

Appendix 9. Pattern - MoM tool

Design activism as a new method for inquiring into mixed emotions in uncomfortable social interaction

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Abstract Over the last couple of years, design activism has attracted increasing attention among designers and design researchers, but the approach seems not to have found its way yet to the Design & Emotion research community. In this paper, we introduce design activism as a new approach valuable for probing into the role of mixed emotions in interpersonal interaction. To set the scene, we critically examine recent sources on design activism in order to provide a general characterisation of what constitute the approach. Next, we argue for how social game can be seen as an instantiation of design activism used, in a current research project, to inquiry into how teenagers feel about visiting their incarcerated fathers in top secure prisons. Finally, we relate our findings to discourse on ambiguous emotions and use this to visualize the eliciting pattern of ambiguous emotions.

Keywords *Mixed emotions, Uncomfortable interaction, Design activism, Disruptions*

Introduction

Over the last couple of years, design activism has attracted increasing attention among designers and design researchers, but the approach seems not to have found its way yet to the Design & Emotion research community. This is unfortunate, because design activism offers a variety of practices, methods and techniques for addressing emotions in their socio-political forms of manifestation – forms that typically falls outside the explanatory scope of design and emotion research.

Design activism's value for emotion-driven design approaches can be identified on at least two levels. At a *macro-political* level, emotions are pivotal, for instance, for the release and configuring of conflicts, upheavals or riots that social movements perform to protest against systems of power, ideology and control. Here design activism has been proclaimed to be a valuable means for achieving benefits for the whole of society or even Planet Earth, for instance, by instigating more sustainable ways of living as an alternative to existing consumerist lifestyles (Fuad-Luke, 2009; Thorpe, 2012). At a *micro-political* level, the feeling of being wronged, discriminated or excluded is often motivating individuals to act in order to resist or modify negative power structures experienced by the individual themselves, their family or community. At this level, design activism has proved to be a useful approach, for instance, for empowering cancer patients to have a say in decision-making processes during their treatment at hospitals (Eva Knutz, Markussen, Mårbjerg Thomsen, & Ammentorp, 2014); for increasing citizen rights and participatory democracy in the shaping of the urban environment

(Markussen, 2013); or for integrating the needs of marginalized ethnic groups into the design of services of public institutions (Lenskjold, Olander, & Halse, 2015).

In this paper, we shall focus on design activism as practiced on the micro-political level. There are two reasons for this. First of all, the majority of studies on design activism have paid attention to the macro-political level. These studies tend to view design activist practices primarily in light of their underlying motivating political cause, notably the globally growing dissatisfaction with neo-liberalism's greed for growth and consumption, the resulting financial and economical crises and the negative impact on our environment (Fuad-Luke, 2009; Julier, 2013; Thorpe, 2012). However, at the micro-political level, we rarely meet conflicts that are determined by an overtly political disagreement. As a matter of fact, it can be fairly difficult in the first place to see that there even is a conflict. Politics, here, is a matter of how power is subtly interwoven into the way in which individuals, in their everyday life, are constrained by systems of authority and control. Therefore, the central questions are: How is people's ability to act, feel and communicate regulated by these systems of power? How do these systems configure roles of identity, and determine who has the power to speak, move and work. Systems of power can be found in the form of public institutions and services (healthcare, education, work) or they can be materialized into physical form as when public furniture is designed to prevent certain societal groups to use them (e.g. homeless and alcoholics). To fathom how designers can help vulnerable groups to escape the limitations and

constraints of power structures, it is necessary to develop an approach enabling them to work with these power structures as a design material that can be subverted, re-modified and transformed.

Our claim in this paper is that design activism represents such an approach, but we need to work out more concise definitions for understanding it. Hence, in contrast to the dominant views, we argue that definitions of design activism according to its political cause and motivation are insufficient. Instead, we suggest that a definition according to its *modus operandi* would serve as a more valid defining criterion. By *modus operandi* we refer to the particular way in which design activism is practiced through disruptions and provocations. To make our case, we start out, in the very beginning of the paper, by critically reviewing some of the current definitions of design activism. On the basis of this, we will then be able to present our alternative definition and how it contributes to the existing body of knowledge.

The second reason for focusing on the micro-political level is that design activism offers new methodologies for researching into mixed and ambiguous emotions. In the D&E proceedings series and elsewhere we have detected a growing interest in mixed emotions, ambiguity and even uncomfortable interaction. However, much of this research has been devoted primarily to developing conceptual frameworks and theory (see e.g. Benford et al., 2012; Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012; Fokkinga, Desmet, & Hoonhout, 2010; Gaver, Beaver, & Benford, 2003), while less attention has been paid to which methodologies are appropriate for investigating these complex forms of emotion in situ.

In this paper, we introduce what we shall call *social games* as a new activist methodology that enables design researchers to gain insight into mixed emotions as they appear in uncomfortable interactions. We have successfully used social games as a method to investigate the ambiguous emotions of teenagers, who are visiting their incarcerated fathers in top secure Danish prisons. As much research in sociology and criminology have made abundantly clear, in-visits programs in prisons are extremely important for the well-being of children and adolescents (see e.g. Beckmeyer & Arditti, 2014; Dunn & Arbuckle, 2002; Kampfner, 1995; Poehlmann & Eddy, 2013). However, what is not well recognized is that the children do not experience seeing their incarcerated parents as unequivocally positive. The happiness or joy of being reunited for a short while is often counterbalanced by negative emotions such as guilt, anger or fear. This is a key finding for developing future programs and visiting facilities.

Our social games have been designed so as to let teenagers play out their mixed feelings and emotions associated with visiting their imprisoned fathers. By drawing on our general reflections on design activism as well as recent theories on critical play and activist games (e.g. Flanagan, 2009) we will explain in more detail how social games can be understood as an activist methodology. In so doing, it will be feasible

for others, working in related areas, to value social games as a method for unravelling emotions in interpersonal interaction. Finally, we will discuss and conclude on how our findings concerning mixed emotions fit into existing frameworks and theory.

Related work on design activism and political design

Design activism is an emergent field that is gaining solid foothold in design research. This is not least evidenced by the proliferation of conferences and conference tracks, special journal issues and books dedicated to the topic. Initially, it might be worth considering how we should generally conceive of activism. According to Jordan (2002, pp. 8–11), activism can be defined as a group of “people acting together outside ‘normal’ institutional channels” in order to transgress and change existing state of affairs according to the desires of those taking action. As a further defining criterion, Jordan says, that “a *disruption* of the pre-existing morality-defining institution can be found” (Jordan, 2002, p. 10 our italics). Hence, we could think, for instance, of Occupy Wall Street as a vivid example of activism, where a group of people disrupts the institutions and capitalist power inhabiting Wall Street as part of a collective protest against social and economic inequity worldwide. However, we need to be aware that design activism is not the same as political activism. As we have argued elsewhere, design activism is not a boycott, strike, protest, demonstration, or some other political act. It “lends its power of resistance from being precisely a *designerly* way of intervening” into systems of power (Markussen, 2013, p. 38). The question is of course what do we mean by ‘designerly’? Let’s go through some recent suggestions to make our own notion stand out more clearly.

It is a widely held belief that design activism should be understood as opposing capitalism’s idea of free markets, consumption and economic growth being the pillars of society. Such a view can be found in Thorpe’s book *Architecture & Design versus Consumerism: How Design Activism Confronts Growth*, wherein she argues at length that design activism is about focusing on design’s social and environmental returns (p. 7), not on the marketplace and sales numbers. In Thorpe’s interpretation, design activism becomes a term that is interchangeable with designing for social innovation and sustainability. And design, for her is then primarily anchored “to physical, material and visual aspects of the built and manufactured environment” that live up to these criteria (ibid.)

However, we argue that Thorpe’s account is confusing. First, even though many design activists would perhaps agree with the agenda, it is unwarranted to use social and environmental sustainability as the essential defining criteria, because it risks confusing design activism with a motley assembly of other divergent practices. Thorpe’s own listing of exemplary activist work within architecture and design throughout the book clearly shows why this is problematic. If we take Thorpe’s definition at face value, Michael Reynolds’ Earth Ships (p. 9) would thus be as activist as Renzo Piano’s California Academy

of Sciences (p. 159). But, as we see it, only one of them qualifies as such, namely the Earths Ships.

Reynolds has revolutionized architectural practice by showing how people, living in areas hit by natural calamities, can rapidly re-build their houses and villages by using simple DIY-practices, garbage and found materials. In so doing, he has made these people independent of architectural companies, the good will of local policy-makers and emergency aid. Renzo Piano's California Academy of Sciences certainly deserves credit for its eco-friendly architecture, but it is not – like Reynold's Earth Ships – the outcome of a practice "outside 'normal' institutional channels". Nor does it show any sign of "disrupting pre-existing morality-defining institutions". On the contrary, it is part of the marketplace that architects nowadays have to respond to with 'sustainability' luckily entering the vocabulary of the client.

Secondly, Thorpe's idea of architecture and design being understood simply in terms of "physical, material and visual aspects of the built of the built and manufactured environment" is exactly what many design activists have problematized. For instance, Awan et al. (2011) argue that the equation *architecture=building* needs to be reformulated, because it represents the idea that a building or produced stuff is the solution to every social and environmental problem. Further, by prioritising aspects of static properties of objects, emphasis is put on visual, aesthetics and the technical, "over which architects still retain nominal control, in terms of being able to manipulate form and technique". In contrast, Awan et al. (2011) argue that architects need to see the loss of control as "an inevitable condition" and that architecture and design is part of a dynamic network of socio-political actors with divergent needs, interests and values. By replacing 'architecture' with the notion of 'spatial agency', the authors underline that the radically new task of architects and designers is to find ways of empowering spatial agents (minorities, citizen groups, communities, and so on) to appropriate public space independently of the constraining structures of society.

Within design studies, a similar critique of the equation *design=products* has been voiced, albeit not in strict activist terms, by Björgvinson, Ehn & Hillgreen (2012; 2010) and DiSalvo (2010, 2012). Björgvinson et al. raise concern that the idea of design being "a tool for the development of functional, innovative consumer products" is unable to appreciate the social-political complexity of today's problems. Instead they suggest conceiving of design as a political "infrastructuring", that is design as processes of change used to modify "the space of interactions and performances and that may be "explored as socio-material frames of controversies, opening up new ways of thinking and behaving" (Björgvinsson et al., 2012, p. 102). On the same note, DiSalvo introduces the term "adversarial design" to denote a design approach that acknowledges an underlying dissensus between agonistic interests and forces as a foundational condition for design in public space.

Following from these observations, it is necessary, as Fuad-Luke (2013) has suggested, to come up with some clearer definitions. According to Fuad-Luke, "The way that design activism levers political change depends upon whether the design approaches set about to encourage dissensus, consensus or both." (Fuad-Luke, 2013, p. 473) Design activism that encourages dissensus is "working outside or oppositional to the existing paradigm", while design activism that encourages consensus is "working within or inside the existing paradigm" (Fuad-Luke, 2013, p. 470). However, we suggest reserving the term "design activism" to denote only design work living up to the first definition. This definition is in line with Jordan's general characterization of activism and underlines that contest, subversion and disruption are at the core of design activism. The second definition is too vague, in our view, because it would apply equally to practices such as design for sustainability, social innovation, social entrepreneurship and social design. All of these fields are commonly defined in the research literature as working within or inside the existing paradigm in order to achieve social or environmental returns (see e.g. Manzini, 2014; Moulaert, 2009; Moulaert, MacCallum, & Hillier, 2013; Phillips, Lee, Ghobadian, O'Regan, & James, 2014). Consequently, it becomes impossible to tell the difference between design activism and these other related approaches.

Yet, what distinguishes Fuad-Luke's work from Thorpe's is that he derives the defining criteria of design activism from a closer scrutiny of its way of operating rather than its aim or motif. More specifically he highlights dissensus as being essential for its *modus operandi*. Interestingly, this bears some likeness to DiSalvo's (2012) notion of 'adversarial design' and Björgvinson et al.'s (2012) notion of Design Things (with a capital T). Both of which denote fields of design conditioned by dissensus, meaning controversies and agonistic forces. However, in their accounts, dissensus is reduced to be a matter of political dissensus, while aesthetic dissensus is neglected. Aesthetic dissensus, according to Rancière (2010) is when artistic practices, including design, are used to re-distribute sensible-material conditions so as to open up the relation between people's action, feelings, and emotions for renewed negotiation. It is the effect, for instance, of heterogeneous objects being brought into social-political space thereby enabling a redistribution of power, control and roles of identity. Reynold's Earth Ships provides a paramount example of aesthetic dissensus. In constructing the Earth Ships we see most literally how sensible garbage and waste materials are redistributed to become valuable building elements. By enabling people, with the use of DIY- techniques, to re-build their own houses the feeling of how they live and inhabit space is also fundamentally changed from negative to positive. Finally, architectural practice works as spatial agency to affect a redistribution of power and control, by emancipating marginalized people from being passive victims to become active citizens taking the spoon in their own hand.

What can be seen in examples like this is that dissensus in design activism deals with political issues, but notice that “stakes of politics”, as Rancière (2004, p. 13) says, are staged through an aesthetic practice as a form of experience. This is the hallmark of what we refer to as a ‘designerly’ way of practicing activism. It is a way that political power can be disrupted and contested through aesthetic practice thereby opening up new ways of living, thinking and communicating.

Social games as an activist research method

Working out more accurate notions of activism in general, and of design activism in particular is a prerequisite for understanding how games can be approached from an activist perspective. In this section, our aim is to demonstrate that not only can games be the resulting product of a design process. They can also serve as a research methodology for uncovering how mixed emotions regulate and shape uncomfortable interpersonal interactions at a micro-political level. Key to this methodology is disruptions and subversions that are able, through the game experience, to open up a gap, to be studied further, between actions, emotions and action tendencies. It is precisely in this sense that the notion of games we will be presenting here differs from what is commonly known as ‘design games’. Design games are usually found valuable as means for involving multiple stakeholders in collaborative processes of design (Bang, 2010; Brandt, 2006). Most often, such co-design processes aim towards the design of products, solutions or services, and the involved stakeholders have more or less clearly identified roles and identities (e.g. client, sub-providers, technicians, end users, designers, etc.). It is a matter of using games to arrive at consensus, to embrace a large degree of complexity defining design problems and to let people influenced by a design solution have a say in the developmental process. In the activist understanding of games, games are not means for co-designing solutions among stakeholders, but for re-negotiating the relations between the people involved and redirecting attention of the inquiry towards a possible re-configuration of these relations. For this reason, we prefer the notion of social games to design games (see also E. Knutz, Lenskjold, & Markussen, 2016).

Elsewhere we have provided a thorough introduction to social games being a rather unexplored object of study in design and game research (Markussen & Knutz, 2016). Hence, in this section, we shall only briefly account for what characterises social games and focus instead on how they can be used as part of an activist methodology. In the next section, we use empirical findings from a case project to further substantiate our argument and claims. This will eventually lead to the identifying of types of mixed emotions, which will be discussed in relation to existing research literature.

Social games are games that are designed to explore processes of socialization or the forming of interpersonal relationships. In social games, play can be used, as Sutton-Smith (1997) has convincingly shown, for the sake of transforming social bonds,

feelings of belonging to a social group or work out social and cultural norms. For the same reason, social games must be distinguished from related game genres such as *serious games* and *health games*. While serious games are designed to train and educate players in solving problems, acquiring new skills and knowledge (Michael & Chen, 2006; Shaffer, 2006; Squire, 2005; Westera, Nadolski, Hummel, & Wopereis, 2008), health games are designed to improve the well-being of the players, for instance to reduce anxiety in children after their parent’s divorce (e.g. *Earthquake in Ziiland*) or to help veterans suffering from Post Traumatic Stress disorder (Helms & Rahbek, 2012). The primary goal of social games is neither edutainment nor health improvement, but to build and negotiate social relationships between the players. This means that social development is the central game goal, and that a nuanced understanding of how play and game may be constitutive for interpersonal interaction is essential.

Another central difference between serious games and health games and social games has to do to with how the games either comply with or disrupt existing power structures. Serious games and health games typically affirm certain hierarchical orders and asymmetrical distributions of control characteristic of the organization and contexts they are designed for: The surgeon plays the role of a surgeon operating on a patient, the pilot play the role of the pilot navigating an airplane, and so on. In contrast, since social games are designed for the sake of overthrowing power structures, they often disrupt social identities by letting people play imaginatively with alternate identities, forbidden identities and even identity switching. For the same reason social games often use fictionalization rather than simulations as is the case with serious games and health games (E. Knutz, Markussen, Desmet, & Visch, 2012).

Within game studies, Flanagan has introduced the term “activist games” to account for “games that engage in social issues, through, most commonly, themes, narratives, roles, setting, goals, and characters; and less commonly, through game mechanics, play paradigms, interactions, or win states to benefit an intended outcome beyond a game’s entertainment or experiential value alone” (Flanagan, 2009, p. 13). More importantly, Flanagan further specifies that activist games always use tactics and elements of subversion and disruptions, that is actions or interventions intended to overthrow “a law, rule, system, condition” (Flanagan, 2009, p. 10). To see how social games can serve as part of an activist research method, it will be useful to look more carefully at how we have used social games in an on-going research project.

Case project: Social Games against Crime

One of the aims of the research project Social Games against Crime is to increase knowledge of how children and adolescents (age 11-18) experience visiting their incarcerated fathers in top secure Danish prisons. Relatively little is known about these children and statistics on their visiting frequency and patterns are sparse. Yet, there are indications that

Figure 1. Left: Signs standing on the parking lots. Right: a top view of how the players cars “drive” around to pick up helpers.

children stop visiting their fathers at the age of 10-11 for various reasons. This is unfortunate, because, as criminology and social research have demonstrated, the sustaining of a positive relation with an incarcerated parent may have a beneficial effect on how children are able to cope with the personal and social problems caused by imprisonment (see e.g. Beckmeyer & Arditti, 2014; Dunn & Arbuckle, 2002; Miller, 2006; Poehlmann & Eddy, 2013) .

In the present study, we will be focusing on teenagers of gang members (the project as a whole focus on a broader target group). Drawing upon the design activist framework we have introduced, it is possible to conceive of in-visits taking place in prisons as involving emotions eliciting on a micro-political level. Remember that, as we said in the introduction, on this level, politics is not about overtly political disagreement and conflicts, but has to do with the way in which authority and control is subtly interwoven into and constraining interpersonal interaction. Often, the effect caused by such constraints makes itself felt as a matter of mixed and uncomfortable emotions.

Having a father incarcerated has similarities with what is described as ‘ambiguity of loss’. Ambiguity of loss occurs when families live through grieving processes, for instance, because of the acute separation of a loved one, divorce, illness, war, terror, or death. According to Boss (2007, p. 105), ambiguity of loss may come in two variants. The first one is when a loved one is physically absent, but is felt as being psychologically present (e.g. this has been reported by relatives to military deployed abroad). The second form of loss is when a loved one is felt as being psychologically absent but is physically present (e.g. this has been reported by relatives to Alzheimer patients). Both forms are distressing, uncomfortable and may traumatize (ibid. 2007).

Children visiting their fathers behind bars are faced with the first condition of ambiguity of loss. Evidently there is more to it than what the physical-psychic

divide can account for. What is important is thus to understand the ambiguous emotions involved and how they play a role in the forming of social relationships between children and their fathers. What are the mixed emotions that children experience as part of in-visits interaction? We shall argue that social games can be a valuable new a method of inquiring into this complex set of questions. Initially, we will describe a social game that was designed as a research artefact to help the researchers know more about the mixed emotions of teenagers who have a father incarcerated for more than ten years in top secure prisons. Saying that the game is a research artefact means that it was designed as a playful form of participation for a target group with the purpose of collecting and documenting knowledge about their inner emotional life. Hence, the game elements were designed in different colours and materials to allow the researchers to backtrack the game process and gather data about each teenager’s individual relationships with their fathers.

Participants and procedure

The participants were three teenagers (age 14-16), two family therapists and two design researchers served as facilitators. The teenagers come from similar environments and their fathers belong to the same criminal gang. The game was used as part of a 2-day game workshop, held at a family consultation centre that offers help to families and children of inmates. The workshop was organized into two parts. In the first part, three teenagers and one family therapist played the game, whereas two teenagers and two family therapists played the game in the second round.

The game consists of a board with a winding road that takes the players round a city. On the road, there are eight parking lots, where the players can park their car to pick up helpers. The parking lots are: “The Treatment Centre”, “The Pub”, “The Tech Shop”, “In the Media”, “Personal Talents”, “On the Street Corner” and 2 “Family and Friends” (see Figure 1). There is also a cemetery where you end up, if one of the other players bumps into your car. Before starting the game, each

Figure 2. Left: Mira's dream and barriers. Right: Niels' dream and barriers.

player must formulate a wish or dream on a card that is then placed on "the Cloud", found on the centre of the board. Next, the players are given three "Barrier Cards" upon which they must write down three barriers that prevent them from fulfilling the wish or dream.

Each player has his or her own toolkit, where there is a "Dream Card" and a car, modelling wax, cotton balls and sticks so that the players can make their own character. The game play consists in throwing a dice to drive around the city and, on the way, pick up helpers who can help you to overcome your barriers. On the parking lots the players can find predefined helpers, but they can also invent their own writing them down on empty "Helper Cards". By throwing a yes/no dice the player determine whether an attempt to break down a barrier is successful or not. On the road there are a number of roundabouts. When landing on them the players must choose roundabout card that makes it more difficult to achieve the goal.

In the following we present our findings gained from playing with two of the teenagers. For the sake of data protection their identity have been blurred, using fictitious names.

Mira is a 14-year old girl. She starts the game by saying that she wishes to see her father less than once a week (the current situation). On her Barrier Cards she writes that it will be "difficult to tell him", that "he gets disappointed" and cannot see the situation "from her point of view". To overcome these barriers she mentions, when she lands on the "Family and Friends" spot, that she would like her father's friend Jacob to assist her when she is going to tell him that she does not want to come as often. Jacob is a former gang member, but is still highly respected by the father. When she lands on Personal Talents for the first time, Mira recognizes that she will need "better speech

gifts", the second time it is suggested – with a smile – by one of the other players that she could perhaps use "hypnosis" to convince him. (Figure 2)

During the play Mira shares with the family therapist and other teenagers that she is afraid, that when she tells her father that she will not come as often, he will call some gang members and ask them to break up her current friendships with other girls and boys. He knows that by disclosing that she is the child of an incarcerated father, many of Mira's girl friends would simply stop seeing her. Mira feels threatened and controlled, but at the same time that telling him is best for her well-being.

Niels is a 14-year old boy. For over a year, he has not been visiting his father in prison, because of a dramatic episode: the father was calling some gang members outside prison to have them threaten Niels' mother. But now Niels is slowly making contact again, because he wants to see his father. On his Dream Card he writes that he would like "more reasonable visits" (Figure 2). Asked about what he means by "reasonable" Niels says that he doesn't want to talk to his father about problems with his mum or the elder brother who is a drug addict. Reasonable to Niels is, for instance, when he fights with his father in the visiting room and they toss around chairs. Then, he really feels being close to his father; that his father is psychologically present and loves him.

On his Barrier Cards, Niels identifies three barriers that stand in the way of achieving the reasonable visit. His father is "unable to see when he is wrong"; "he doesn't understand why Niels says that he needs a break", and he's annoyed about Niels being accompanied by his foster father" (at the age of 14 children are not allowed access to prisons in Denmark without being accompanied by an adult). That makes things complicated.

Discussion

The game we designed for this project can be regarded as an activist method for at least two reasons. First of all, it makes visible the power structures and control that the fathers exert over their teenage children. Notably, this takes the form of threats of breaking up their relationships if the teenagers do not do as the fathers please. Secondly, while this certainly evokes negative emotions like fear and anxiety in the children, they also experience positive emotions when seeing their fathers. By playing the game the teenagers not only become aware of these emotional tensions; they also work out a set of strategies for how to re-configure the relationship with their fathers according to their own needs and wishes.

We can get a better grasp of this if we turn towards some general conceptualizations of mixed and ambiguous emotions. Fokkinga and Desmet (2012) have proposed four main clusters for describing mixed emotions, which are useful to accurately describe how emotions regulate the ambiguous relation of the teenagers with the fathers. Hence, they distinguish between mixed emotions manifesting themselves as in i) 'unrelated emotions' where positive and negative emotions are evoked by different situations or objects, and no mutual interdependency can be detected; ii) 'ambiguous emotions' occur when positive and negative emotions are elicited by the same situation or object; iii) positive effect of negative emotions is when negative emotions has a certain positive effect on either the person's experience of the situation, their attitude towards the situation or their behaviour, which in turn leads to a positive emotion; and iv) 'negative effect of positive emotion' is when positive emotions have a negative outcome. Due to limited space we will not go into each one of these clusters here. Instead, we will concentrate on how Mira's and Niels' social bonding with their fathers can be further explained as forms of ambiguous emotions.

For Mira the visiting situation evokes two opposite, yet closely interrelated emotions and action tendencies. On the one hand, the prospect of visiting her father to tell him that she will not come as often, is evoking anxiety and negative emotions, because she fears his threats and hence she feels reluctance to go and see him (action tendency 1). On the other hand, she feels torn, because she still wants to keep a good relationship with him and continue seeing him, just not as often. This is evoking a positive emotion and an action tendency 2, which is in contrast to the negative emotions. Using the diagram of Fokkinga and Desmet (2012) this can be depicted as in Figure 3.

In Niels' case, ambiguous emotions are also at stake in regulating how he relates to his father and the prospect of visiting him again. Niels is experiencing negative emotions of the visiting situation when recalling his father discussing problems about his mother and brother with him (stimulus). Previously he has shown that if he feels too much pressure he will actually stop coming to the prison (action tendency 1). Yet, at the same time Niels is eager to change this situation so that he gets reasonable visits in the future, perhaps he can fight with his father, which he

Figure 3. Ambiguous emotions as identified in Mira's and Niels' stories. Adapted from Fokkinga & Desmet (2012).

feels very positive about (action tendency 2). Like in Mira's case this is causing ambiguity between two opposite emotions and action tendencies.

Fokkinga and Desmet's framework is useful for explaining not only mixed emotions, but also how they are involved in configuring uncomfortable interpersonal interaction. Thus, the object evoking ambiguous emotions can be a person, a situation or the relationship between two persons. In this sense Fokkinga and Desmet's framework contribute with a dimension that is absent from some other existing frameworks found within Design and Emotion. For instance Markussen (2009) identified ambiguous emotions being central for understanding the use of technology in healthcare, but here ambiguous emotions were analysed as a tension between mentally elicited and embodied emotions not as a result of social interaction. Earlier we have introduced a distinction between fictional and real emotions in order to account for how a computer game could be used to help small children cope with the ambiguous emotions they live through when being hospitalized (E. Knutz, 2012, 2013; E. Knutz & Markussen, 2010). But again, in this account, the social dimension of emotions was left out of attention.

Interest dedicated to mixed emotions has also appeared in HCI and interaction design. Gaver et al. (2003) pointed out years ago that ambiguity could be a resource for design in the sense of designing "products and systems to become psychological mirrors for people, allowing them to try on new identities or to question their values and activities". But in Gaver et al. (2003) ambiguity is most of all a matter of conceptually challenging effect being narrowly

conceived of as a relation between people and products and systems, not as a social relationship between people. The same is the case with Benford et al. (2012) who have argued that “deliberately engineering discomfort”, can be “a way of creating intense and memorable interactions and engaging with dark and challenging themes” (Benford et al., 2012, p. 2005). In Benford the social is only conceptualized as rites de passage, processes where the individual go through critical transitions to become member of a group. Yet, the teenager’s visiting their father is not about them going through a rite de passage. They engage in dark and challenging themes, but they struggle to figure out whether they should continue seeing him. It is a different concern.

Interestingly, however, what both Gaver and Benford call attention to is that ambiguity and discomfort may have a similar effect as dissensus and disruption. They open up for a new formation of identities (Gaver) and for engaging with dark and challenging themes (Benford). In our social game these effects result from activist elements of the game. Thus, it is allowing the teenagers to untie the bond between their actions (visiting) and how they feel about these actions. In so doing, a more fine-grained view can be gained of what exactly is causing the feeling of uncomfortable interactions.

Conclusion

In this paper we set out initially to provide a more concise definition of design activism. After providing a critical review of some of the existing literature on design activism, we suggested that design activism could ideally be seen as a design practice evoking dissensus and the overturn of pre-established macro- and micropolitical structures. By defining it according to its modus operandi, we argued that it is possible to distinguish design activism from the closely related disciplines such as social innovation and social entrepreneurship. Secondly, we exemplified how social games can be seen as an example of an activist methodology taken in the sense that these games may disrupt entrenched roles of identity, the habitual coupling of action and emotions, saying, doing and feeling. The value of such a methodology hopefully became evident in our account of how the social game could be a viable way of probing into the nature of ambiguous emotions. Thus by playing the game, teenagers were able to inform us about their feel towards visiting their incarcerated father. More specifically, we got a more precise view of how mixed emotions pertaining to visiting situations in prison may conflict with each other. How emotional conflicts evoke different kinds of action tendencies and uncomfortable interactions. By accounting for this, we hope to have shown how design activism can find its way to the Design & Emotion research community.

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'Feeling good' unpacked: Developing design tools to facilitate a differentiated understanding of positive emotions

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Abstract The range of positive emotions experienced in human-product interactions is diverse, and understanding the differences and similarities between these positive emotions can support emotion-driven design. Yet, there is little knowledge about what kind of tool would be effective to leverage the differentiated nature of positive emotions in a design process. The current study explores the possibilities to develop design tools that facilitate a nuanced understanding of positive emotions and the considerations for developing such tool. Four new tools were developed that were different regarding how they described distinctiveness of positive emotions, formats, and usages. This paper introduces the tools and reports a focus group study that investigated when and how the tools would be of use in design processes, and their strengths and weaknesses.

Keywords *Design for emotion, Positive emotion, Design tool, User-centered design*

Introduction

Imagine yourself as a designer having a kick-off meeting with your client. The client asks, "Please design a mobile payment service that makes people feel good." You commit to the challenge and return to your design studio. You talk with your colleagues about the project and suddenly find that they look a bit puzzled. One designer asks, "What do you mean by 'feeling good'?" He continues, "Do you mean confidence, curiosity, or amusement? These are all pleasurable feelings, yet different. Which ones do we need to address?"

This is an exemplary snapshot of when distinguishing nuances between positive emotions becomes an issue in a design process. We can experience a myriad of different pleasant emotions when interacting with products, and it has been found that being aware of differences between them can be advantageous for designers (Desmet, 2012). For example, it can be helpful in deliberately determining positive emotions to design for upfront in a design process and supporting communication about users' emotional responses to a product within design teams, with clients, and with users (for an overview of the benefits of differentiating positive emotions in design, see Yoon, Pohlmeier, & Desmet, 2014).

Then, how can we help designers be aware of nuances of positive emotions and use this understanding for their practices? Perhaps, taxonomies of positive emotions that can be experienced in human-product interactions (e.g., Desmet, 2003; 2012) could serve as a repertoire to choose from when specifying emotional intentions of a design. Or having an overview of the

different causes of a set of positive emotions (e.g., Campos, Shiota, Keltner, Gonzaga, & Goetz, 2013) could help understand the underlying conditions that evoke certain positive emotions. In design research, various types of design tools and techniques have been introduced with an intention to make theoretical knowledge assessable to designers and to inspire designers in user-centered design activities, e.g., card-set, experience prototyping (Buchenau & Suri, 2000), and design documentary (Raijmakers, Gaver, & Bishay, 2006). Although diverse, it has been unexplored what type of tool would be effective to leverage the differentiated nature of positive emotions in a design process and how such tool could be developed.

In this paper, we explore how a nuanced understanding of positive emotions can be facilitated with the aid of design tools. It was expected that the resulting insights could clarify (1) what kind of tool would be appropriate to apply for a certain design activity (e.g., understanding user emotions) and (2) what needs to be considered to develop such a tool. Thus, the research question is: how can nuances of positive emotions be conveyed to designers by means of a design tool?

This paper begins by describing the research approach and developments of four design tools. The next section reports the results of two focus groups in which design experts reviewed the developed tools and discussed when they could be useful to apply, along with their strengths and weaknesses. Based on the results, this paper ends with a discussion on limitations and recommendations for future research.

Empathy	Affection	Aspiration	Enjoyment	
Sympathy, Kindness, Respect	Love, Admiration, Worship	Dreamy, Lust, Desire	Euphoria, Joy, Amusement	
Optimism	Animation	Assurance	Interest	Gratification
Courage, Hope, Anticipation	Surprise, Energetic	Pride, Confidence	Inspiration, Enchantment, Fascination	Relief, Relaxation, Satisfaction

Figure 1. Typology of 25 positive emotions categorized in nine emotional types (adapted from Desmet (2012)).

Approach

Given the fact that there are few design tools available that facilitate a nuanced understanding of positive emotions that can be used as a reference, we decided to take ‘research-through design’ as a main approach. Research-through design refers to a research method in which building and testing prototypes take center place and becomes the key means in constructing knowledge (Stappers, 2007).

We decided to develop a set of design tools, all of which helps distinguish various positive emotions in a different manner, and analyze them with design experts to identify their advantages and disadvantages. Four prototypes of design tools were conceived: positive emotional granularity cards, emotionPrism, emotion raconteur, and emotion carousel. These tools were based on the typology of positive emotions (Desmet, 2012) that includes 25 positive emotions that can be experienced in human-product interactions (see Figure 1). The tools were conceptualized to be different regarding how they describe distinctiveness of positive emotions, formats, and usages. The following parts of this section describe the developed tools.

Developing design tools

Tool 1: Positive emotional granularity cards

Positive emotional granularity cards (Yoon, Desmet, & Pohlmeier, 2013) consist of 25 cards that incorporate definitions of emotion labels, the general conditions where people experience certain emotions, and visuals of emotion expressions. Each card represents a

positive emotion. In line with Wallbott (1998) who showed that behavioral manifestations are indicative of a particular emotional state, it was assumed that providing visuals of behavioral manifestations and concrete contexts could give a comprehensive understanding of the emotions in the set. The visuals used in the card-set includes, for example, a group of people being proud of winning a game and a man being relaxed listening to music. For each emotion, four different images were used. The chosen images were validated to check if they could effectively characterize the target emotions, and whether they were distinct from other similar positive emotions. A detailed description of the validation procedure can be found in Yoon et al. (2013). All emotions have unique ‘core relational themes’ that represent the conditions that elicit them (Lazarus, 1991). Core relational themes of the 25 positive emotions were formulated to describe the eliciting conditions from appraisal theory-based literature and printed on the cards (for an overview, see Yoon et al., 2013). For instance, core relational themes for respect and surprise are “a praiseworthy character of someone conforms to internal or external standard” and “something unexpectedly happens beyond one’s expectation” respectively.

Tool 2: EmotionPrism

The tool, ‘emotionPrism’ consists of movie-sets, which illustrate how people interact with a product when expressing the 25 different positive emotions in these interactions (Yoon, Pohlmeier, & Desmet, 2016). This tool was devised based on the insight that positive emotions are characterized by distinct behavioral

Figure 1. Typology of 25 positive emotions categorized in nine emotional types (adapted from Desmet (2012)).

Figure 3. Screenshots of movies (from left: joy, enchantment, and love) and the interface of the emotionPrism.

tendencies (Fredrickson, 2013). For example, joy stimulates playful interactions, and kindness makes the interactions tender and protective. We postulated that having a tool that communicates the differentiated behavioral tendencies could support designers to purposefully envision user behavior concerning particular positive emotions, and to stimulate different types of usage behavior. It was decided to use hands interacting with an artifact as a channel to discriminate between positive emotions since most human-product interactions involve hands. The movie-sets were generated through an exploratory study with professional actors manifesting positive emotions, e.g., squeezing, groping, and caressing. Instead of showing a specific product in the videos such as camera or lamp, this tool uses a neutral cube that symbolizes a product in an abstract manner to make the application of the tool not limited to the design of a particular product type. Four movie-clips were generated for each emotion, and validated through online surveys (for the details of the validation process, see Yoon, Pohlmeier, & Desmet, 2016). Designers can use the movie-sets incorporated in the tool to discuss what kinds of usage behavior would be appropriate or desirable for a design context and a product, and to select a set of relevant positive emotions accordingly by referring to the movie-sets as a repertoire to choose from.

Tool 3: Emotion raconteur

'Emotion raconteur' is a sound library of users' anecdotes. The anecdotes were collected from actual users' experiences in which they had felt positive emotions when using products (Desmet, 2012). The anecdotes illustrate how a product plays a role as a

cause of an emotion in a certain context and how users react to it. For instance, an anecdote used for the emotion 'sympathy' was "sometimes I see an old car that has been damaged and taped with glue. The owner does not seem to have enough money to repair properly it. I imagine how difficult her life is and feel sympathy." The idea behind this tool was that, as argued in Demir (2010), anecdotes that depict certain emotional experiences can help designers be aware of antecedents of emotion, i.e. what caused the feeling, and in a narrative, distinct emotions can be well perceived at the sentence level beyond simple valence classification (Buitinck, van Amerongen, Tan, & de Rijke, 2015). It has been proven that some specific positive emotions can be identified via vocal cues, e.g., affect bursts of admiration and laugh with amusement (Schröder, 2003). Since emotions expressed in an anecdote can be more accurately and quickly communicated when they are supplemented by paralinguistic cues such as voice tone inflection (Epley & Kruger, 2005; Pell et al., 2015; Sauter, McDonald, Gangi, & Messinger, 2014), we decided to voice-record the anecdotes with professional voice actors. Each emotion involved three to four anecdotes (86 in total), and the recorded audio files were incorporated into an audio application in which the anecdotes can be navigated based on emotion type and product type.

Tool 4: Emotion carousel

Emotion carousel is a package of three interactive installations, 'Assurance', 'Enjoyment', and 'Interest', each of which enables designers to explore three similar positive emotions in an interactive way (nine emotions in total). We assumed that in line with Buchenau, M., & Suri, J. F. (2000), offering firsthand experiences of particular emotions in a physically staged setup could give a visceral sense of differences between the emotions.

Assurance

This tool intends to show what it is like to feel confident, courageous, and proud in interactions. The tool consists of several interactive steppingstones placed apart on which a person can step. When he/she goes up a steppingstone, it gives a pleasant sound with a light effect, confirming that it is safe to jump on, which would make him/her confident to keep stepping forward. When he/she encounters a stone, at a distance of one meter, the stone on which he/she stands gives a signal that it is doable to reach the next one through light and sound effects, which also gives an inviting signal. This would lead him/her to forge ahead with courage. After going through all

Figure 4. A screenshot of the app through which the anecdotes can be played.

Figure 5. A participant interacting with the installation 'Assurance'.

Figure 6. Participants interacting with the installation 'Enjoyment'.

steppingstones, they start celebrating by blinking the lights and playing songs. This would give a sense of achievement, facilitating a feeling of pride.

Enjoyment

This tool intends to evoke three emotions: joy, amusement, and euphoria. The tool consists of a series of soft balls connected to each other. When a person touches a ball, a light comes to his/her hand and leaves again. The slowly breathing light would encourage him/her to follow it and gently pat the ball. While doing this, the tool explains through a speaker that sensorial pleasure could give a feeling of joy. Then, the tool invites him/her to the game 'catch me if you can' intending to evoke amusement. Lights start fast moving and jumping, challenging him/her to catch them. When a light is grabbed, it stays in the ball. As several lights are moving, it requires involving additional players to catch all moving lights, which would make the interaction more socially playful. While doing the game, the tool explains the feeling they are likely to have, which is amusement. When all lights are caught, all balls start flashing on and off to

signal the successful end of the game. This accomplishment gained through the joint efforts would make the experience euphoric.

Interest

The Interest has a large sphere in which a series of lights and speakers are nestled. By changing its behavior, it shows three different conditions where people would experience enchantment, fascination, and inspiration. For enchantment, the sphere hangs out of a person's reach putting him/her in a passive position and mysteriously glows emitting slow sounds. After a while, the sphere comes down and invites him/her to get close to it; a spot starts blinking and attracts him/her to touch. When touched, another spot starts flashing, building a pattern of lights. While doing this, he/she would get fascinated and become curious about what kind of pattern he/she will end up. After this cycle, the inspiration phase starts. The sphere gives him/her the opportunity to create his/her pattern of lights and melodies by touching different spots. This would encourage playing with it and inspiring to express his/her creative ideas into a form.

Figure 7. Participants interacting with the installation 'Interest'.

Assessing the developed tools

While all four developed tools are meant to provide a broad repertoire of positive emotions, they address different aspects of emotional experiences and use varied forms, which implies that they might have different strengths and weaknesses. We postulated that depending on the type of design activity, e.g., communication of users' emotional states or specification of emotional intentions, to some degree, the usefulness of each tool would differ. For example, the images used in the card-set would help designers grasp and imagine the situations the emotions arise while the movie-sets used in emotionPrism, which was made abstract and decontextualized would stimulate designers to conceive the effects of emotions on interactions.

Two focus groups were conducted in which the developed tools were reviewed by a panel of design experts, focusing on how the tools could contribute to helping designers discern a variety of positive emotions, when the tools would be useful to apply, and their strengths and weakness.

Method

Procedure

Three mixed groups of design experts participated in the study: four design teachers, four design professionals, and one emotion expert. The design teachers and emotion expert were recruited from the faculty of Industrial Design Engineering of Delft University of Technology. On average, the design teachers had 28.3 years of experience in education and the emotion expert had 6.5 years of experience in emotion-driven design research. The design professionals were from four design consultancies and self-identified their roles as a usability engineer, industrial designer, interaction designer and user researcher. On average, they had 4.5 years of experience in design practice. The emotion expert was in charge of guiding the participants to keep their focus on emotions during the sessions, not being distracted by other subjects such as technologies harnessed in the prototypes. The participants were recruited from the authors' professional networks and were paid for their contribution.

The focus group consisted of three phases: learning the topic of the study, reviewing the prototypes of the tools, and discussing their characteristics. In the beginning of the session, the first author explained the benefits of discerning and articulating nuances between positive emotions for designers based on the findings in Yoon et al. (2014), and the purpose of developing tools. Next, the participants watched demonstration movies that illustrated how designers used the tools. The prototypes of the tools were placed on a table, and the participants were guided to try them out. Although the prototypes of 'emotion carousel' were presented, the computational components were left inactive due to the intricacies of installation setting.

The participants then discussed each tool in comparison to others regarding the ways they account

for differences between positive emotions, e.g., descriptive and experiential. The tools were reviewed in turn, and the participants described in what kind of design context the tools would be useful, along with their strengths and weaknesses. They made suggestions regarding additional issues that should not be overlooked for developing a new tool. Each session took two hours and was audio-recorded.

Data analysis

All audio recordings of two focus groups were transcribed verbatim and coded based on the context of tool application, strength, weakness, and suggestions. In the analysis of the transcripts, the emphasis was given to identifying themes concerning the relevance to how the nuances of positive emotions were explained, instead of the prevalence within the transcripts, e.g., general impression of the fidelity of the prototypes. In the process of analysis, data related to general considerations for design tool were left out, e.g., size, time and budget available, and location of use.

Results

Overall, the participants agreed that designers could benefit from being aware of differences between positive emotions in various design activities. The concepts of the developed tools were well accepted and the elements incorporated in the presented tools, e.g., pictures and videos, were seen to be carefully selected and relevant inputs that can serve as a reference or an education material. They were convinced that designers and design students could use the given tools to learn multi-faceted aspects of positive emotions. In this section, the main strengths and weaknesses perceived by the participants are reported with the examples of their quotes. Table 1 gives an overview of the main findings.

Positive emotional granularity cards

"It helps me describe how I actually feel. I would never come up with 'admiration' or 'love', and likewise, people have a lot of troubles expressing their emotions. People just say "that's good" or "I am happy with it"." (Participant 2)

Provision of a broad palette of emotion labels combined with pictures and descriptions appeared to have a potential to deepen emotion knowledge and minimize the risk of misleading interpretation. Participants pointed out that the emotion labels would ensure unambiguity and support articulation of emotional states with fine-grained terms, which would provide designers with a shared language of emotions, facilitating clear communication. The card format was particularly appreciated, as it was effective to share and arrange the contents with others. The participants found the pictures useful; (1) the pictures would give designers a quick overview of positive emotions and help them decide to further look at the detailed information, and (2) the elements illustrated in pictures, e.g., context, product, and people, could support designers to infer when and how particular emotions arise.

While useful, the descriptions of emotions were considered a bit abstract and difficult to compare. Most of the participants agreed that the textual information would not be gone through because designers tend to be more attracted to visual stimuli in their creative processes. The card format was seen to be limiting in helping designers to understand experiential aspects of emotion, e.g., a behavioral and physiological influence of an emotion. The selection of the pictures was considered critical; some cards included culture-sensitive ones, leaving room for wrong interpretations, and the diversity of examples that illustrate emotion-eliciting situations were to be ensured.

EmotionPrism

“This tool can be used for an interaction design course. It helps students understand... how I can translate an interaction quality into a movement of or with an object. Then, the emotion words don’t matter that much.” (Participant 6)

The participants responded that the tool well demonstrated differentiated usage expressions in relation to emotions and, it could be used as a repertoire of various interactions qualities. They mentioned that the several videos could support designers to identify and explain specific feelings that the interaction with a product should bring for the user. The participants particularly favored the

abstract representation for this purpose. Also it could guide translation of the intended positive emotions to interaction qualities and physical form of a product because the videos could give a hint of what product properties could be effective to afford an interaction that expresses certain emotion.

The weaknesses of the emotionPrism were that some positive emotions were inappropriate to express with only hands. The participants suggested that some emotions, e.g., euphoria and excitement, might be better expressed by showing a full-body of a person. To reenact some emotions, e.g., hope and dreaminess, narratives seemed indispensable. Since the videos only demonstrate how emotions influence behavior, when and how those emotions arise remained unclear, which appeared to be problematic, as the tool gives partial information about an emotional experience.

Emotion raconteur

“From the story, I discovered different types of love – not only love between two people but love with an ugly object from a grandfather. It shows you can also design for that kind of experience.” (Participant 6)

The participants regarded the voice recordings as one of the strengths of the tool; the voices in the narrations clearly conveyed a user’s emotional states and seemed to facilitate empathy with him/her. All participants agreed that the professional voice actors’

Table 1. An overview of the suggested design activities, strengths, and weaknesses.

Tool	Design activity	Strength	Weakness
Positive emotional granularity cards	— To deepen designers’ emotion knowledge	— Minimize the risk of misleading interpretation	— Abstract descriptions of emotions
	— To use a shared language of emotions within a design team	— Help articulation of emotional states with fine-grained terms	— Difficult to compare the descriptions
EmotionPrism	— To translate the intended positive emotions into interaction qualities	— Effective to share and arrange the contents with others	— Not useful to understand experiential aspects of emotions
	— To understand the relationship between emotion and behavior	— A quick overview through pictures	— Unclear expressions of some emotions
	— To specify interaction effects to address	— Help infer when and how particular emotions arise	— Do not explain the causes of emotions
Emotion raconteur	— To facilitate empathy with users	— Provide a repertoire of various interactions qualities	— Unclear expressions of some emotions
	— To help stakeholders understand the intended emotions to design for	— Demonstrate what product properties could be effective to afford an interaction that expresses certain emotion	— Do not explain the causes of emotions
Emotion carousel	— To provide an education material for students	— Vivid expression of emotions	— Take a long time to go through all anecdotes
	— To inspire designers (as a collection of examples that show how design evokes particular emotion)	— Stimulate to imagine actively what the user and situation would look like	— Emotions are not comparable
Emotion carousel	— To provide an education material for students	— Give a visceral sense of differences between emotions	— Do not give an overview of emotions
	— To inspire designers (as a collection of examples that show how design evokes particular emotion)		— Difficult to remember the emotions experienced while using the tool
			— Difficult to communicate the nuances of the feelings
			— Less applicable in a professional context

recordings made the anecdotes credible and lively, stimulating them to imagine what the user and situation would look like. The concrete product examples were particularly appreciated in that they helped easily understand how a product could play a role in eliciting particular emotions. Given these advantages, the participants mentioned that this tool would be effective in helping stakeholders of a design project, e.g., client, understand the intended emotional experience the design needs to facilitate, and empathize with their target users.

Since it takes a long time to go through all anecdotes and they are incomparable, the participants responded that this tool would not be supportive when a designer wants to have a quick overview of the positive emotions; the tool is more useful when a few positive emotions are already determined to focus on. The participants noted that an extra care should be paid to the generations of the recordings. Some recordings sounded too polished and stereotyped, which made less authentic and inspirational.

Emotion carousel

"Sometimes we realize something when we actually do. How I feel through my body - I can't get it from reading a book. Reading '30 degrees of temperature' is different from actually being in a warm room" (Participant 5)

The strength of the emotion carousel reported by the participants was that first-hand experiences of particular positive emotions through interactions with artifacts could give an intuitive sense of differences between them. The direct experience would enable designers to reflect the feelings they had, the qualities of the interactions, and the conditions where the interactions were enabled. This tool was seen to be a major advantage for those who study emotion-driven design. One participant mentioned that the experiential quality of the tool would enable design students to learn and open up their mind that various emotions can be experienced in the interactions with a product. Moreover, the tool itself could serve as a collection of examples that shows how product properties (i.e., shape, size, behavior, and color) can be manipulated to evoke a particular emotion.

However, the participants pointed out that some people might be unaware of or not clearly remember the emotions they experienced while using the tool, and would find it difficult to communicate the nuances of the feelings. Besides, people's emotional responses may largely differ due to different meaning attribution or current mood. The participants criticized that the concept of the tool seemed less applicable in a professional design context.

Additional findings

The participants reported that the given tools would play their roles as a resource, but there would be an added value in using a tool as a mediator that motivates active learning about positive emotions. They suggested two approaches: (1) making 'making' as a part of a tool and (2) contemplating. The

participants noted that the iterative process of designing for particular positive emotions in person may lead designers to ponder upon the conditions that evoke them, how users perceive it, and how product properties could be manipulated to facilitate those conditions. Besides, the participants suggested that designers could grasp subtle differences between positive emotions by discussing their retrospective real-life memories.

The four tools were perceived to be limiting in providing a comparative overview of positive emotions. The participants found this issue critical; they postulated that depending on a criterion, the similarity between positive emotions can be differently arranged, and ensuring multiple entry points for exploring and comparing the emotions could be advantageous. Some examples given by the participants were classifications based on interpersonal versus non-interpersonal emotions, eliciting conditions, effects on behavior, and how long the emotions last, i.e., durations.

Discussion and conclusion

This paper sheds light on the topic of designing for nuanced positive emotions with a focus on how a differentiated understanding of positive emotions can be facilitated by using design tools. The focus group study with design experts examined when and how the four types of design tools would be of use in design processes, and their strengths and weaknesses were discussed. In general, the purpose of developing tools was well accepted, and the participants could relate the practical benefits of applying the tools with various design activities such as communicating emotional intentions, envisioning effects of emotions on behavior, and increasing an empathic understanding on particular emotional experiences.

All four developed tools were considered useful to understand differences between positive emotions in a fine-grained manner, yet they were regarded different in terms of the application possibilities, strengths, and weakness. There was no single tool considered effective for all of the suggested design activities. Each tool appeared to have varied strengths and weaknesses, and their usefulness differed depending on the type of design activity. From this observation, we believe that the comparative overview of the four tools emerged from the study (see Table 1) could give an insight into what kind of tool would be appropriate to apply in design processes; a designer could choose a proper one by referring to specific design activities and strengths that each tool is associated with. In addition, the identified advantageous (and disadvantageous) aspects of the four tools could serve as design considerations for developing a future tool. A new tool could be conceived to avoid certain disadvantageous aspects of the four tools or to integrate several advantageous aspects that may corroborate the other in supporting a particular design activity.

The focus group study comes with some limitations. The study aimed to clarify when and why to use the developed tools, but the scope of the discussed design

activities was somewhat narrow. Although designers can benefit from a nuanced understanding of positive emotions across all stages of a product development process (Yoon et al., 2014), most of the referred ones during the study were mainly focused on the activities in the early stage. This might be due to the setup of the study; if the participants were provided with a model of a design process, e.g., human-centered design process (ISO, 2010) and was guided to use it as a reference during the discussion, the results would have been more thorough and specific. Although the 'emotion carousel' is an experiential tool, meant to evoke certain positive emotions through physical interactions, it was reviewed only based on a demonstration movie. One participant mentioned that it was hard to conceive how designers could benefit from using it without a direct experience.

We expect that actual applications of the developed tools in various design projects will allow us to better understand how designers perceive and experience the tools, which will help us further improve the tools and the findings reported in this paper. In particular, within the suggested tool applications, there were some activities that involve non-designers such as a client and an end-user. Although the participating design experts suggested that the tools could be effectively used in collaborative activities, it is uncertain whether other stakeholders of a design project would equally value the tools and be willing to use them. Therefore, it is required to delve into other stakeholders' views on tool applications and involve them in devising new tools and techniques.

While exploratory, this study provides the first insights into how designers can be supported to work with a differentiated understanding of positive emotions with the help of design tools. We will refine the current tools based on the collected suggestions and continue to explore ways to support designers in their efforts to deliberately create positive experiences.

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Poetically rich experiences: The interplay between affect and cognition

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Abstract Poetry is one of the oldest forms of art used to facilitate emotional experiences through imagery. In poetic form, ordinary experiences become intriguing, engaging and mentally challenging. With its many positive effects, poetry has much to offer to experience designers. Experience-driven design is a field that steadily seeks innovative ways to enrich product experiences. The current paper is lead by the proposition that understanding the intricate nature of everyday poetic experiences will inspire design for rich experiences. Borrowing perspectives from the fields of art, philosophy, psychology, and experience design, it introduces a new notion of 'poetically rich product experiences' and concludes that poetic richness emerges from unusually high and concurrent stimulation during cognitive and affective processes underlying product experiences. Understanding poetic richness will provide designers deeper insights into the expressive nature of products. Consequently, products can assume a unique poetic function that triggers users to bodily respond and intellectually reflect on daily phenomena abstracted into poetic experiences.

Keywords Poetry, Rich product experience, Ambiguity, Cognition, Affect, Experience design

Introduction

Poetry emerges from everyday events common to all humans and is a unique medium for artistic expression. Sources for poetic experiences are often sought in natural events as exemplified in Figure 1. Although recreating poetic experiences through objects is generally considered an intrinsic goal of art (Hunter, 2002; Williams & Harvey, 2001), poetry has found a rightful place in interaction and experience-driven design (Santokhi, 2014; Ling, Chang, & Liang, 2011; Liang, 2013; Faroughi & Faraoghi, 2013; Marti, 2015). Designers' interest in poetry comes from the noticeable effect of observed poetry on people rather than poetry as literary art. By evoking rich affective responses in people and simultaneously challenging their intellectual capacities, poetry moves people, leaves them in a state of awe, wonder, fascination and/or inspiration. The everyday moments that have such strong positive and lasting effect on people are therefore called *poetic*.

Neither designing for positive effect nor designing for rich experiences is new in the field of experience-driven design (see research concerning mixed emotions by Desmet & Fokkinga, 2012, metaphoric meaning by Cila, 2013, or pleasurable sensory experiences by Blijlevens, 2011; Hekkert, 2006; Özcan & Schifferstein, 2014). However, existing studies and good examples of design for rich product experiences have not yet considered 'richness' in its extreme state and its positively overwhelming effects on users. Analysing the poetic snow moment with the traditional terminology of experience-driven design research (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007; Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008; Desmet & Stappers, 2011) leaves us

with the following preliminary definition for *poetic*: Anything *poetic* induces concurrently active and extremely competitive affective and cognitive processes pertaining to *aesthetic appreciation*, *discovery of new meanings*, and *implicit emotional connotations*. Thus, existing knowledge regarding rich product experiences is unrepresentative for poetically rich experiences because so far richness has been investigated through the lens of one unit of product experience (e.g., aesthetics only) rather than holistically (i.e., aesthetics, meaning and emotion all together as an experience). Through literature review in the fields of art, philosophy, psychology, and experience-driven design and analyzing existing objects that are designed to evoke (poetically) rich experiences, this paper presents first reflections on poetic richness as an experience to design.

Need for something poetic?

Our daily lives offer us a range of ordinary-to-exciting moments facilitated by designed objects (i.e., products). While some events such as making a cup of coffee or cycling to work can feel ordinary because they are part of the routine therefore nothing is notably unusual; other moments such as driving fast in an electric Tesla or discovering a new way of cooking with Le Creuset pans can feel exciting or even adventurous. It is very rare for people to experience poetic moments, similar to the snow example in Figure 1, especially induced by designed objects. Objects are traditionally designed to respond to basic human needs, i.e., physiological and safety needs as proposed by Maslow (1954). With the developments observed in the history of design and technology, utilitarian products have become mundane and expected in users'

Figure 1. Imagine a poetic moment. You are about to step into fresh snow; everything around you is crisp white and deep blue; the blue and the white are connected by branches of frozen trees; the sun is shining and reflecting on frozen but soft land; you craved to be part of that perfect untouched scene, now you are there and realize that your desire to become a part of the scene will make the perfection imperfect and that the imagined is better off as imagined than as experienced; while your imagination made the beauty your existence will defy it. What do you do? Time stands still. You contemplate to take the first step; you desire to prolong the white beauty by immersion, because destruction stays behind and the beauty waits ahead. And you discover: without experience there is no imagination. You step into fresh snow leaving a trace, not only in the snow but also in your memory, not only in the past but also in the future. (Author's imagination).

daily lives. The next big step in design history was to include users' affective responses to the designed objects (e.g., Holbrook & Hirschman, 1982; Mitchell, 1995) and make the design process more user-centered. The following trends were design for emotion, pleasure, interaction and experience (Overbeeke & Hekkert, 1999; Desmet, 2002; Norman, 2004; Hekkert, 2006). Nowadays, the technically perfected products are expected to be at least pleasurable and preferably offer a certain experience (see Figure 2) as was proposed by Pine and Gilmore (1998) as 'the experience economy'. In this vein, design for meaning has become another important ingredient to consider when designing product experiences (Govers & Mugge, 2003; van Rompay, 2008; Cila, 2014). Objects designed for experience not only indulge human senses and intellect instantly but also fulfill higher-order human needs such as 'autonomy, popularity, and stimulation (Hassenzahl et al., 2010; Özcan & Sonneveld, 2009; Özcan, 2014). Thus, the richer the experience is the more impact it will have on people's striving for a better live and a better version of themselves.

Poetry, in the sense of verse, is one of the oldest forms of art used to facilitate emotional experiences through imagery. Poetry enhances subjective-wellbeing (Hunter, 2002; Kreitler & Kreitler, 1972) by transcending moments, moving people, and transporting them into fictional worlds (Rosenthal, 1974; Selincourt, 1976). Furthermore, poetically rich moments induce creativity, facilitate learning, improve critical thinking, develop empathy and insight, and interrupt people's ordinary routine by offering them novelty, discovery, and untargeted emotions (Parr & Campbell, 2006; Routman, 2000). In poetic form, ordinary objects can become intriguing, engaging and intellectually challenging; or novel objects can feel fascinating and inspiring and invite people for interaction and explorations. Therefore poetry offers people richer experiences and longer-lasting effects.

Poetry and experience design

Poetics does not have a long history in the field of interaction and experience-driven design and only a couple of studies systematically investigated the role of poetry in design. The effect of poetry has been considered with practical demonstrations of how poetry can inspire design by providing means for narrative expressions (Desmet & Nauta, 2006; Marti, 2015) and by comparison of the creative procedures of poetry and design (Beatty & Ball, 2011). Santokhi (2014) investigated the phenomenology of naturally occurring everyday poetic experiences in order to provide designers with a set of principles to be considered when designing for poetic effect. These principles are the following: vastness (size and number of the stimulus) inspires awe, defamiliarization (looking at familiar objects from an alien perspective) leads to dissociation and estrangement, déjà vu (feelings of slight familiarity in an incongruous context) leads to confusion, ambiguity (multiple interpretation caused by perception) causes intrigue, and metaphorical representation brings new perspective. Furthermore, all these internal events have the capacity to evoke visceral emotions noticeably felt in the body.

Liang and colleagues (Ling, Chang, & Liang, 2011; Liang, 2013) have focused on the quality of interactions occurring between people and interactive objects and spaces. Ling, Chang, and Liang (2011) suggested poetic devices for interaction design such as importance of context, ambiguity (hidden object expressions), and elusive object properties (intangible materials) that would help trigger the process of imagination. Liang (2013) later suggested that poetic quality of interactions is constructed through imagination based on blocking people's ability to reason.

The doctoral study of Ionascu (2010) argued the place of poetics in design practice and suggested that poetic objects are "experimental artefacts that investigate the

Figure 2. Sony 'be moved' campaign states that Sony measures success with 'the flutter of a heartbeat and a bead of cold sweat' and that it is about what they make people feel not what they make.

everyday life of contemporary culture" and that it is the users that assign the function of such objects during experimentation and discovery. Similarly, Dunne and Rabby (2013) consider design as debate and designed objects as vehicles to carry ideology and initiate speculations about current issues in the world or future scenarios in utopias. Ionascu's as well as Dunne & Raby's stance is also relevant for the discussion on the thin line between art and design. As Munari (1966), a designer and an artist, argued that art should not be exclusive to galleries and museums but should be part of everyday life and that designers are equipped to create the same gratifying effect as art objects do (i.e., art experiences).

Although these studies introduced the need for 'poetry in design' and emphasized the added value of poetic approach on the richness of the product experience, they also pinpointed a lack of principled theory regarding poetry in experience design. Therefore, theory and practice-based knowledge is necessary concerning the quality of richness, strong psychological effects and relevance for behaviour/attitude change evoked by poetic product experiences. The ultimate goal is to enhance well-being; more specifically, to brighten people's day by offering them a sudden rush of positive feelings and thoughts within the familiarity and comfort of their everyday environment.

Rich experiences: From ordinary to poetic

Users' experiences involving designed objects can be discerned into three groups: *erfahrung* (cumulative knowledge), *erlebung* (momentary affect), and *erlebnis* (meaningful event) (Desmet & Stappers 2011; Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008; Hassenzahl et al. 2004).

Erfahrung stems from experiences based on established practices and familiarity. If one has once driven a car, then that person has experience in driving; the more people drive the more experience they gain. Design for usability, ergonomics and co-design are concerned with such practical experiences. *Erlebung* is the experienced affect, a response, caused by an external stimulus in a certain situation. Driving an electric car may be experienced as 'exciting and joyful' or 'boring and superfluous' depending on the mindset of the driver and their context. Such product experiences have been researched and designed the most frequently in the

context of experience-driven design (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). These experiences are further explained with three types of affective and cognitive responses: aesthetic appreciation, attribution of meaning, and emotional responses. *Erlebnis* is a holistic experience, an event, which can be narrated as a story. Driving the U.S. Route 66 in a Mustang to discover the American psyche can be a 'confronting' experience. The trigger of such experiences can be a salient object (e.g., a Mustang car) but the configuration of other relevant objects, people, and contexts further adds to the quality of an *erlebnis*. Highly abstract and complex concepts such as sustainability, luxury, love, thrill, and grief are more apt for such experience design.

Thus, the notion of richness in relation to experience differs for *erfahrung*, *erlebung* and *erlebnis*. For *erfahrung*, richness may be the fluency in various actions when operating a product. For *erlebung*, it may be the strength of bodily feelings and the amount of mental activity when interacting with products. For *erlebnis*, it may be the overall pleasantness experienced through the variety of noticeable small or big events. From the perspective of affect and cognition, it is expected that experiences get richer from *erfahrung* towards *erlebung* and *erlebnis*. *Erfahrung* experiences are utilitarian by nature and more involved with sensory-motor skills and less with affect and cognition. *Erlebung* experiences are affect- and meaning-laden by definition and the strength of affective responses and semantic associations can be manipulated through design. *Erlebnis* experiences offer a series of *erlebung* experiences and their richness is intensified by quantity and quality of sequentially occurring various experiences.

However, when investigating poetry of everyday events, Santokhi (2014) showed that participants described poetic experiences both with *erlebung* and *erlebnis* experiences (see Figure 3). For example, the sensation of light bath foam is poetic because the temptation to touch the foam makes the foam disappear (*erlebung*); or the mating dance of mayflies is poetic, because mayflies, upon years of preparation, create a magical scene while mating which symbolizes desire as much as sacrifice in the form of death (*erlebnis*). Both kinds of experiences pertain to richness experienced as a result of enhancing an

Figure 3. Two images exemplifying daily poetic experiences from Santokhi (2014) study. Images taken from Santokhi's Pinterest board 'poetic experiences'. www.pinterest.com

ongoing perceptual or cognitive process (i.e., deepening the *erlebung*) or altering the primary percept through a broad conceptual activity (i.e., broadening the *erlebnis*).

The dictionary definition of *richness* relates to large quantities, abundance, interest caused by variety, and pleasantly deep or strong sensory input (colour, sound, smell). This definition also suggests that richness is preferable because of its salience and associations to positive valence. A product experience is also considered rich when it has a significant positive effect on the user on an aesthetic, emotional, and meaning level. Fokkinga and Desmet's (2013) definition regards richness as noticeable positive impact on the user caused by mixed emotions (i.e., both positive and negative). Thus, richness is also achieved by the inclusion of negative affect. Cila's (2013) version tackles the multiplicity of meanings associated to one product through metaphors. Others consider richness in terms of intensity of multisensory pleasure (Blijlevens, 2011; Hekkert, 2006; Özcan & Schifferstein, 2014). Richness in interaction Poetic richness is often symptomized by the intensity of the felt effect. Certain moments in life can feel so overwhelming that people's time perception alters, their senses are highly stimulated or movements are slowed down; people feel puzzled as well as encouraged to take it all in and reflect on what just happened.

Poetry encountered in everyday lives is mainly about experiencing strong emotions as a result of a deep meaning searching process triggered by an aesthetically pleasing object. Thus, when searching for poetic richness, it is central to equally consider the contribution of affect (i.e., aesthetic appreciation and emotional response) and cognition (meaning attribution). It sounds logical to analyze ordinary experiences in this order too. That is, perception leads to sensory (dis)pleasure and cognition, which

ultimately affects the emotional state. However, in poetic experiences these sequential processes either unusually overlap or there is a continuous loop which updates previous mental states and feelings (Santokhi, 2014). In either case, poetic experiences cause concurrently occurring mental activities and bodily responses attributed to either one salient object (as in *erlebung* experience) or a series of objects (as in *erlebnis* experiences). As a result affect and cognition compete for sense making and bodily resources such as attention and capacity of action come short in creating an overwhelming feeling.

Affect, cognition and poetic experiences

Affect and cognition are always intertwined in the appreciation and comprehension of art objects (Silvia, 2005). Poetry, like other forms of abstract art, aims to express an affect-laden concept (e.g., love, success, grief, equality) through stimulation of senses, emotions and mental imagery in order for people to virtually experience the concept based on their previous experiences and knowledge (Shklovsky, 2009; Williams & Harvey, 2001). Starkey (2008) suggests that one needs to feel during an experience in order to fully understand it and reflect on it. During an episode of a particular experience people build new semantic links among objects and make new discoveries of meanings (Dervin, 1992; Kolko, 2010). If experiences are emotionally salient, then affect and meaning are associated and attributed to the objects facilitating the experience in a certain setting; these associations can also have a metaphorical nature (Lakoff & Johnson, 2008).

In poetic experiences, pleasure and intellectual challenge are closely connected; thus, experiencing poetry is a rewarding problem solving activity. Aesthetically salient and novel objects / events induce imagination and facilitate creative thinking, and therefore are preferable in everyday life. However,

there needs to be a trigger for the 'poetic' chain of reactions to take place. Aesthetic salience (either positive or negative) works as a good trigger because if perception results in high sensory (dis)pleasure then people become intrigued. For example, perceptible novelty draws attraction (Bianchi, 1998). Previous research (Silvia, 2005; Tan, 2000) has indicated *interest* as an emotion and an aesthetic response observed in psychology of art. Because, the appraisal of art objects is not grounded in satisfying basic needs but in satisfying higher-order needs such as need for mastery, learning, pleasure. In art objects, while aesthetic salience evokes interest (Cupchik and Gebotys, 1990), such interest is sustained by an intensive cognitive process which overloads the information processing capacity and delays comprehension (Ribeiro, 2013). Interest and delay in comprehension contribute to the affective tone and amount of mental imagery, strength of immersion and meaning making (Green & Brock, 2002). The feelings of 'time freezing' or 'being speechless' derive from the delay in information processing and retrieval.

So far in the paper, affect has been used as a general term to cover both aesthetic appreciation and emotional response. In terms of artful experiences, the distinction between the terms is not great. Aesthetics pertains to perceptual processes and is the gratification of senses; therefore, it is considered a disinterested pleasure when experiencing art (as suggested by Kant). Artists play with basic perceptual rules (e.g., complexity, novelty, symmetry) in order to create interest considering the people's repertoire of existing percepts (Hekkert, 2006). Emotional responses to art differ from emotional responses to ordinary (designed) objects. Scherer (2005) describes art-driven emotions as aesthetic emotions because such emotions (e.g., being moved, awed, or full of wonder, fascination, bliss) occur in the absence of goal appraisal and are produced by the appreciation of the intrinsic qualities of objects/events. This is further supported by the model of aesthetic appreciation and aesthetic judgment by Leder, Belke, Oeberts, and Augustin (2004). Leder et al.' model further suggests that preliminary identification of object as art (i.e., pre-classification) alters the emotional affective state of the of the viewer and frames their appreciation of art through continuous affective evaluation. Furthermore, aesthetic emotions, perhaps feelings, are also present in poetic experiences due to conceptual association and experiences to previous emotional episodes (Juslin, 2013).

Cognition follows perception and cognitive processes intend to recognize, categorize, and identify the percept. Cognition happens when conceptual associations start to emerge from semantic memory even in the absence of clear recognition or identification. For art objects, vagueness in identification, i.e., ambiguity, is preferable. As ambiguous percepts induce several nodes in sensory memories, possible configurations of objects and mental imagery start to emerge (Pavio, 2010). Moreover, natural links of conceptual association also start to emerge among the activated nodes. A wide range of conceptual activation and imagery is the aim

Figure 4. Ecology of ordinary product experiences.

of art objects following the common phrase 'art is thinking in images' (Shklovsky, 1990). In observations of art objects meaning attribution is replaced by meaning making (AKA sense making) processes. Therefore, the more ambiguous the object is the more mental search it needs to be made sense of. Metaphorical representation is another way of creating ambiguity because of the multiplicity in meaning. Moreover, poetry, a literary art, uses words to entice mental imagery, visual or musical arts use sensory input. Although it would be faster to access sensory memories via images or sound, semantic activation will be more delayed; and vice versa via poetry (Özcan & van Egmond, 2007; Özcan & van Egmond, 2009). Therefore, the imagery might be more vivid and pronounced with poetry, but senses would be more active and busy with sounds and images. Eliciting experiences through designed objects will probably activate more sensory and less semantic information; consequently affective feelings and feelings of familiarity may dominate a poetically rich experience.

Framework for poetic experiences with products

The challenge for designers is to understand how to create poetry with objects using their own set of knowledge, rules, and tools. Designers' basic knowledge pertaining to experience design (i.e., aesthetic appreciation, meaning attribution, and emotional response) mainly derives from research into psychological foundations of art (Cupchik & Gebotys, 1990; Dewey, 1934). Thus, in broader terms the interplay between affect and cognition are again central to creating poetically rich experiences. However, in a poetic experience that is by definition rich, designers would be aiming at eliciting an extraordinary activity between affective and cognitive processes that are all together gratifying. As a result, poetry experienced with designed objects would have the same function of observing art (e.g., poetry, music). That is, to momentarily transport people into an alternative world enhanced by pleasure, imagination, and feelings as a result of interactions with a limited set of physical input.

Figure 4 presents the elements that constitute the ecology of product experience by emphasizing on the inherent relationship of *product* and *user*. For an ordinary experience to happen users need to *interact* with products. These interactions can be on the level

Figure 5. Ecology of poetically rich product experiences.

of product features, product function, and product context. Physical interactions (e.g., seeing, hearing, touching) trigger multi-sensory processes and conceptual activation. Through such information processing users aim to *identify* the product (meaning), its characteristics, and its purpose, which in return *affects* the user (aesthetically / emotionally). The interactions that take place facilitate *product experiences* on *aesthetic, meaning, and emotional level*. *Context* influences the outcome of the experience as much as *users' and products' inherent characteristics*. The ecology of product experience resembles the user experience model of Thüring and Mahlke (2007) in a way that product and its context are considered as input for mental (affective and cognitive) processes which lead to user response. In line with this, McCarthy and Wright (2004) consider user experience as sense making process taking on five consecutive stages: anticipating, connecting, interpreting, reflecting, appropriating, and recounting. Thus, product experience is actually a holistic and complex mental process and many different components or elements need to be considered in order to understand the output as experience.

Figure 5 presents a similar ecology for poetic experiences. However, Figure 5 emphasizes on the fact that when interacting with poetically designed objects, users heavily rely on their past experiences with the world which is necessary for mental explorations and making sense of the poetic object and the elicited affect. Similarly, Law and colleagues (Law, Roto, Hassenzahl, Vermeeren, & Kort, 2009) also suggest user experience as the subset of 'everything we experience' in the world. Thus, there is a continuous loop between the current interactions and a repertoire of interactions that had already taken place; as a result, users are momentarily transported into fictional worlds laden with affect and chockfull of meaning.

Theoretically, in a poetically rich experience, all the aforementioned three product experiences

simultaneously compete with each other creating an unusually high stimulation on sensory and cognitive. Two main conclusions are the following (see Figure 6). A product experience is poetically rich when both of the following conditions are met: *i.* an object / event has an overwhelming effect on users, and *ii.* users concurrently experience a strong aesthetic response, ambiguity / multiplicity in associated meaning, and intense aesthetic emotions. Figure 6 makes use of constructs that are already familiar to the domain of experience design and research. Emotions have long been considered in design and experience of products (see, Overbeeke, Djajadiningrat, Hummels, & Wensveen, 2002), so is aesthetic experience of products (Hekkert, 2006). It has also been acknowledged that the sub-experiences of aesthetic pleasure, meaning making, and emotional response are complimentary to an overall product experience (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). However, in current design practices and academic research regarding product experience, these sub-experiences are still designed for or studied in isolation from each other for financial, pragmatic, and contingency reasons. With poetically rich experiences (Figure 6), design practitioners / researchers are encouraged to consider and study the cumulative effect of sub-experiences of aesthetics, meaning and emotions on users and its magnitude.

Implications for poetically rich experience design

How can poetic design contribute to creation of novel experiences or enhance existing experiences? While there may be others, two options seem readily plausible considering the literature review. First, designers can choose to either enhance an ordinary object or an event and turn its qualities into poetic or create brand new objects or events that addresses issues that has never been dealt before. Secondly, designers can choose either for *erfahrung* experiences or *erlebnis* experiences with designed objects or events. In the following paragraphs these approaches will be exemplified. Furthermore, Table 1 gives an

Table 1. Design strategies for poetically rich experiences with examples.

Experience	Reason to design	Product	Example	Function*	Effect*
Erlebung	Enhance	Ordinary object	Prosthetics	Awareness	Fascinated
Erlebung	Create	Novel object	Statistical clock	Realization	Stunned
Erlebnis	Enhance	Ordinary event	Feed Love	Intensification	In wonder
Erlebnis	Create	Novel event	ReMind	Contemplation	Inspired

* The contents of Function and Effect in the table are example specific.

Figure 6. Contributors to the poetically rich product experiences. Rich product experiences individually have an effect on the user, poetically rich experiences have a cumulative effect on the user.

overview of the design strategies that may have been used in the creation of poetically rich design examples.

Design examples for poetically rich experiences

Figures 7 and 8 present four experience-driven design examples that can qualify as poetic as proposed in the paper. The examples are organized around *erfahrungs-erlebnis* experiences and novel-ordinary products and events. They are only used for demonstration of the findings of the paper and represent solely the author's opinion.

Beautiful prosthetics

Prosthetic design often feels very clinical and fails to individually represent patients who suffered from body-part amputations. Scott Summit, with 3D-printing technology, offers patients an extraordinary body part which is aesthetically compelling, and extremely desirable. The ornamented metal, glossy surfaces, shape match with the other body part add to the aesthetic appreciation of vision and touch. The new body part is more personal than the lost one because it is custom designed by taking the patient's personality and taste in aesthetic objects into account. The 'beautiful prosthetics' is an update to the older norms of prosthetic design and offers patients fascinating experiences which was unimaginable before. A negative *erfahrungs* experience caused by a standard prosthetic is now experienced as highly positive and awkwardly desirable. In the long-term Summit's design approach tackles the issue of stigmatization by shifting paradigms. It even encourages people to discuss traumatic experiences altering the focus to more constructive topics than the traumatic incident.

Statistical clock

Dunne & Raby offers a highly ambiguous object. Statistical Clock, a black wall-mounted object that vaguely resembles a lamp, mysteriously utters a number once in a while (e.g., one, three). The aesthetics of the object invites to solve the puzzle of the

mysterious of sound and shape which feel dark and gloomy. Once the users discover the meaning behind the speech, they get stunned and their percept is taken to another level. The numbers uttered in the speech represents fatalities mediated by technology (e.g., cars, trains) in an abstract way. People realize that only a technological device can announce death in the coldest way possible whereas human can relate to the importance of lives people had. As people construe the meaning of life and imagine the lives that are lost and warm feelings and sadness start to emerge. As such, a new *erlebnis* experience is created via a device that invites people to question the (im)material value of human life. Are we numbers? Are we humans?

FEED LOVE

Marije Vogelzang designs eating events (*erlebnis*). In FEED LOVE events, she enhances an eating ritual by introducing unusual objects and altering the setting. A relax setting is created for a couple of strangers, one of which feeds, the other eats, with white sheets covering not only table but also the person who is eating. This white veil, the aesthetic object, has an opening accentuated by a warm coloured circle (e.g., yellow or pink). Only the food-giver can see the food, neither party can see each other's face. The food-receiver feels protected by the veil, which facilitates a more open-minded attitude. The setting is awkward but becomes invisible when the couple starts talking about childhood memories induced by the taste of food. As the olfactory senses are intensified, the imagination goes riot and conversation gets deep; which altogether creates a very intimate and loving atmosphere. As a result, both strangers are left in wonder.

ReMind

With ReMind, a pleasurable troublemaker, Jan Brechmann materializes a highly abstract and complex concept, i.e., procrastination. ReMind is deliberately created for people to physically see the consequences of procrastinating so that they are prompted to reflect on it. ReMind is a wall-mounted large wooden ring with round tokens (pucks) and it

Figure 7. Two examples for ordinary objects and events enhanced to facilitate poetically rich experiences. Top: Beautiful prosthetics, 3D printed customized prosthetics, by Scott Summit, 2011 (https://www.ted.com/speakers/scott_summit). Bottom: FEED LOVE, an intimate platform for strangers to feed each other and converse about childhood memories, by Marije Vogelzang (<http://www.marijevogelzang.nl>).

Figure 8. Two examples for novel objects / events created to facilitate poetically rich experiences Left: Statistical Clock, facilitates reflections on technologically mediated fatalities, by Dunne & Raby, 2007 (<http://www.dunneandraby.co.uk>) Right: ReMind, facilitates reflections and actions on procrastination, by Jan Brechmann, 2013 (<http://www.pleasantroublemakers.com/#/remind/>).

turns clock-wise. The act of rotation represents time and pucks represent each personally set goal (e.g., run 6 km, call mother). The top has a barrier, when a puck makes a full rotation and reaches the top it falls. In other words, unattended events pile up and eventually create a mess by falling. This is an analogy for real-life procrastination. ReMind offers a novel ritual by connecting to people's personal lives, goals and hopes for attitude and / or behaviour change. By visualizing a mental process such as procrastination, ReMind aims to provoke reflections on one's behavioural tendencies, priorities, and time-management skills. This new ritual can be considered as an *erlebnis* experience as its impact reaches out to several different events and people.

Conclusions and future studies

This paper presented arguments for the type of richness poetic experiences may offer to users, illustrated poetic effects, suggested application domains for poetically rich experiences in the context of subjective wellbeing, and discussed consequent positive behavior / attitude change. The main argument for poetic richness was the holistic experience of sense making initiated by highly active and concurrent affective and cognitive processes. The underlying proposition is that similar to art, design can potentially help invoking poetic experiences in its own capacity by enhancing people's daily object and social interactions.

From the societal perspective, the objective is to enhance people's wellbeing with the help of poetic design. Poetry in specific and art in general has positive impacts on people (e.g., feeling refreshed, enlightened, enchanted). The function of poetic moments is to provide people with novel experiences through pleasurable intellectual challenge. By facilitating extraordinary experiences that are unfamiliar, poetic objects can offer people opportunities for amusements, realizations, and inspirations. This is an important distinction from ordinary human-product interactions. Similarly, poetic products can be designed to evoke momentary self-reflections that connect people to 'essence of life' and to underlying basic psychological processes that make people 'feel, understand, and react'. As a result, poetically rich experiences can help people to better lead their lives, enable them to see daily events differently, and act accordingly. Such attitude change is desirable, for example, for the stressful contexts of healthcare, travel, and work-life balance.

Furthermore, designing poetic experiences for ordinary objects (i.e., enhancing the experience of an existing object) may have future consequences (Sonderregger, Zbinden, Uebelbacher, Sauer, 2012) in that the aesthetic experience may wear out over time and the object may become unappealing. However, increasing the value of an ordinary object will still have more positive consequences than negative; because, the increase in the value of a daily product will also create conditions for product attachment and love (Russo, 2010).

Overall, theoretical and empirical findings pertaining to the fields of art, linguistics, human psychology, and experience-driven design yield opportunities for the application of poetic experiences and a well-studied new category of products will emerge that has the distinct goal to facilitate poetically rich daily experiences. Understanding poetic richness in such a way will provide designers deeper insights into the expressive nature of products and its power to elicit imagination and feelings. Consequently, design can assume a unique poetic function and make artful experiences more accessible to people's daily environment. Such product category will also trigger a discussion on artful experiences for the masses and whether the value of poetics will be appreciated or lost if poetry is experienced in daily environments rather than premeditated artful contexts.

The paper was heavily theoretical with some design examples in order to set the scene for poetics in design. An empirical study is being prepared to measure the hypotheses that *i.* poetically rich experiences are overwhelming and *ii.* the overwhelming feeling drives from concurrently experienced high aesthetic (dis)pleasure, ambiguity/multiplicity in meaning and strong aesthetic emotions. A set of products/events is being designed for the empirical study. The study will also compare naturally occurring poetic experiences to design induced poetic experiences in order to see the power of design in achieving extraordinary experiences.

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Emotional and rational aspects of the morphogenesis of multimedia presentation - 'user model' and 'viewer model'

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Abstract An approach to the creation of multimedia presentation is described in which presentation is considered as a rational/emotive, logical/imaginative and informatics/compositional formation. Primary attention is given to an artistic structure of the multimedia presentation, the prospects offered by its interactive potential, the interrelation of spatial and temporal organization with the logical organization of an interactive hypertext message, and the relationship between artistic and logical means of expression. Logical construction of multimedia is considered in a five-level system based on a synthesis of the research in the field of information architecture. The system levels are compared with the levels of compositional organization derived from the analysis of empirical material.

Keywords *Multimedia, Hypertext, Composition, Means of expression, Perception*

Introduction

Multimedia presentation

Presentation is a delivery of essential information about a person, organization, service, or idea in a logical and a visual form simultaneously. Multimedia presentation is a specific delivery, which is structured in an electronic hypertext multidimensional space and interactively developing in time on the two-dimensional screen. This definition is equally applied to the local and network editions (e.g. websites). As opposed to changeable web-based multimedia (such as a blog), multimedia presentation is a complete art form.

Multimedia presentation is a framework for storage, transmission, and delivery of information. Due to the integration of logical and imaginative expressive means, this form of message is likely to be the most effective. The present study of morphogenesis of multimedia presentation is an attempt to understand the laws that control the multilevel organization of an electronic publication turning it into an effective message.

Two aspects of perception: rational side and emotional side

Presentation is a kind of multimedia electronic publication, which is a document existing in a virtual environment. As a document, presentation bears informative, communicative, and cumulative functions (Bulatova, 2008). Each of these functions has both discursive and imaginative aspects. From the discursive point of view, the text of the presentation should be constructed logically, conceptually, intelligibly, uniquely, and consistently. This kind of

information is transmitted sequentially and is perceived by the person (i.e., the recipient, the addressee) from a rational standpoint. Shaped as artistic meaning the message of the presentation is constructed integrally and pictorially; it should be created as a completed picture of a 'model of reality' (and this model should be generated by the addressee) (Lotman, 2005). Artistic meaning of the message is transmitted throughout the structural modelling as a whole. Message takes the form of a sign, a symbol, 'an image that ... [is] perceived concurrently, simultaneously in all its parts' (Meshchaninov, 2008). This kind of information is transmitted instantly and perceived by the person (the recipient) from an emotional standpoint.

Thus, the logical side of information delivery is perceived rationally and the imaginative side is grasped emotionally. Cumulative implementation (synthesis) of discursive and imaginative communication determines the set of rational and emotional perception of the message. This creates a high degree of approximation of interpretation by the addressee of the information that has been sent him by the sender. Two pieces interwoven and shaped as artistic design creations produce one masterful end result.

Two communicating aspects operate on the principle of complementarity, holistically delivering the content in the form of a presentation. The holistic form of presentation is created in the synthesis of discursive and imaginative expression. We believe that in the case of directly integrated multimedia communication, the holistic form is realized as a result of synthesis of an informational/programmatic organization and

corresponding compositional organization.

Two aspects of forming messages in interactive multimedia: the informational/programmable side and the compositional side

On the side of informational/programmable organization, a logical structuring of the message data in hypertext is performed. On the side of compositional organization, an artistic structuring of messages in the virtual space-time environment is performed.

On the one hand, a scientific approach is applied to information structuring, but on the other hand, the artistic approach takes the lead.

Science and art are called 'the two ways to explore the world' (Lotman, 2005). One could compare them with 'two eyes of human culture, the difference (and equality) of which create the bulk of our vision'. Let's examine both points of view. We, scientists, examine the natural processes, and then organize congenital processes and repeatable phenomena. We, artists, explore the untravelled road and create an experience of both what had happened and what may or may not happen. A scientific way for the development of a multimedia presentation is to organize the data and the algorithms of interaction with the data by means of hypertext. An artistic way is to create a certain mythological-symbolic context in a multimedia virtual environment. An experience at any point in the study of this art is exactly the moment of understanding.

A virtual space-time environment allows one to use expressive means of spatial, temporal, and spatio-temporal, as well as synthetic forms, of art. However, it should be mentioned that the Russian researchers of multimedia (Demidova, 2006; Filippov, 2003; Jatsuk, 2009; Pakhomova, 1988; Shchitova, 2004), who recognize the audio-visual artistic nature of multimedia, place the visual aspect in first place. Moreover, as a matter of common knowledge, the American scientists have shown the following: a perceptual speed of information coming from reading or hearing, is only 100 bits / sec, while in the case of visual information this parameter reaches 200 million bits / sec (Light Feather & Aznar, 2011, p. 36).

Thus, visual communication can be assessed as the most effective, and this fact informs the direction of our work, mainly in terms of visual means of expression.

Whereas the term 'New media art', which includes such genres as 'Computer graphics' and 'Digital art', etc., has already entered the dictionary, it was not until 2012 that multimedia presentation was considered as an art form developed according to its own canons. The author of the present work 'generated awareness about a multimedia presentation as a new type of art' (Adobe Design Achievement Awards Gallery, 2012), and described the principles of its aesthetic organization (Zyrianova, 2011a), where the rational and emotional constituents combine.

Figure 1. Informational/programmable organization suggested by J. J. Garrett.

For understanding the rational elements of user experience in web design and software development, Garrett's model ('Elements of User Experience') has become a reference for web and interaction designers (Garrett, 2002). Surprisingly, this succinct diagram has proved to be useful for projecting decorative, performative, and media arts, and with certain modifications has been extended to the artistic means of expression and artistic patterns of organization, representing the 'Elements of Viewer Experience' (Modular Design Biennale, 2013; Zyrianova, 2011b, 2014). Merged together, the rational 'User model' of J. J. Garrett, and the emotional 'Viewer model' developed by the author revealed both general and specific laws of composition of multimedia presentation.

Results and discussion

Informational/programmable organization

The information technology, abstract-logical, aspect of designing multimedia has been explored by Garrett (2002), Goto and Cotler (2004), Nielsen (2003), Rosenfeld and Morville (2002), and Phyo (2003). The authors demonstrate the rules of constructing a hypertext information space of the electronic publication and interactive user interface on the screen — in terms of science.

J. J. Garrett describes the process of website creation from the standpoint of the software interface and structuring the information space (hypertext system). Methodology largely affects the scientific side of design rather than the artistic. Garrett considers the process from idea to implementation of the project and highlights five levels of 'user experience' on it. The levels are mutually specified, wherein they are arranged in a certain sequence. The first level (1) is 'strategy', which sets the design goals and targets. The second (2) is 'scope' (both content and functional specifications), which selects the information units and the options for combining them. The third (3) is 'structure', which defines the information architecture and the interaction scenarios with the user. At 'skeleton' (4), the navigation (interaction logic) is developed, the interface (methods of interaction) is refined, and information design (structure) of the page is advanced. The upper (5) 'surface' compiles the information treated at the early levels and establishes sensory communication between the final product and the user. Schematically, the process of product formation is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2. Informational/programmatic organization in our edition.

We consider this scheme as a basis for the abstract-logical aspect of designing a presentation. The particularity of the artistic organization forms of multimedia presentation led to particular modifications in the scheme of informational and programmatic (informatics) organization. The scheme has been modified in co-ordination with the works of Rosenfeld and of Phyo, as well as with the results of the experimental work of the author.

Considering the model of information and multimedia presentation software organization, we also distinguish five levels: (1) 'strategy', (2) 'scope', (3) 'hypertext structure', (4) 'navigation and interface', and (5) 'layout'. Unlike Garrett's model, this model separates the design logic and interaction methods (4) of the design structure of the page, moving the latter to a separate (5) level of organization (Figure 2).

The fifth level of Garrett's scheme, the level of visual organization, in our work is brought beyond the information and software schemes and is fixed in the scheme of composite organization, as shown below. The other parts of the two models essentially coincide.

Our proposed model takes into account two aspects of hypertext interactive communication structuring: the hypertext system and the software interface (informational and programmatic). Figure 3 shows that the 'scope', on the information side, includes the content, whereas on the program side it incorporates the options for the program content links. The 'hypertext structure' deals with information architecture and interaction design. At the next level, the navigation within the information space and the software interface interaction take place. The information and software components are linked at all levels in the layout and are presented to the user in the publication.

Compositional organization

In order to explore the artistic side of the organization, we turned to the fundamental works of Lotman (2005) and Kagan (1972). Lotman claims that art is essentially a simulation activity. Art creates an analogue of reality — an artwork. An artwork is created in a certain system, in its characteristic form of expression, and using a characteristic artistic language. This means that an artwork is realized as a certain material substance. Kagan states that an artwork arises, appears, and presents itself to the

Figure 3. Two aspects of informational/programmatic organization.

viewer as a material design: as a conjugation of the colour patches, volumes, sounds, words, and movements.

Based on the form of expression, Kagan classified art into three groups: plastic (or space), spatio-temporal, and temporal art. He especially highlights a fourth group: synthetic skills combining the features of the three major groups. Web design technology allows one to use a variety of information media: text, graphics, photos, 3D graphics, video, animation, sound, and telecommunications. Information can be submitted in the form of appropriate arts: literary works, planar images, three-dimensional graphics, video narration or animation narration, music and voice tracking. Thus, the electronic form of expressive means can handle a wide range of arts and can work as a synthetic form of art.

An electronic form as an art form was first discussed in 1993 when, after a visit to Silicon Valley in California, the artists John Heemskerck and Dirk Paesmans created the website *jodi.org*. The site was positioned as 'the website-as-an-art-work' (Tribe & Jana, 2006). The artists followed the example of the Dadaists who were manufacturing collages from magazine clippings. For the collages a variety of electronic images and html-codes, sliced and mixed, were used. Widget messages in this symbiosis acquired a new meaning and artistic expression, which, in this case of preventing the perception of the initial information, carried new artistic information: about the irrationality of Dada philosophy.

The authors of the site *jodi.org* have mainly aimed at graphic means of expression. Aside from the graphic language, artistic information in multimedia can be transmitted by means of the literary language, the language of exposition design, and cinematography.

An electronic presentation, or site, can be regarded as spatial art when we pay attention to the graphical design of the page, and to the way in which the information is structured in the virtual space (information architecture), as a durable and spatial-durable one when we observe a step-by-step variation of audio and video content of the screen. It is, however, a special novel form which offers a variation of plot lines and screen contents owing to a special novel technique: interactivity.

Web as a space system	Web as a temporal system
GRAPHICS	MONTAGE
TYPOGRAPHY	SCREEN DYNAMICS
VIRTUAL SPACE	HYPertext PLOTS
ART MATERIAL	INTERACTION
CONCEPT	

Figure 4. Spatial and temporal aspects of compositional organization.

How can one compose all these tools in one system? We do this by correlating, in other words, by drawing parallels between the spectrum of artistic means of expression, and the means of informational/programmatically organization of multimedia presentation.

Drawing parallels

Multimedia presentation provides the possibility of combining various types of art form into a single form. A multimedia product creates an analogue of reality in several systems simultaneously. Its complex structure is formed by the combining and subordination of partial structures from various arts.

Drawing parallels, superposition and projection of the expressive means belonging to various art forms on the software aspect of organization allows one to organize the expressive means of a multimedia presentation.

In this paper, a comparison is made of the informational/programmatically, and compositional sides of the formation of multimedia presentations. Levels of the composite organization of presentation are determined during the transfer of expressive means of formally similar arts to the levels of logical organization.

The shaping in the logical organization of multimedia presentations is decomposed into two aspects: hypertext system and software interface (Figure 3). An abstract logical organization of data is accompanied by their organization in a definite shape. At the same time there is a correlation between the abstract information and a definite spatial construction, as well as a correlation of abstract programs and a definite temporary construction. Strategy is developed in parallel with the concept. Whereas the content and the functionality are the material from which a work of art is created. The information architecture and the hypertext plots form both a virtual space and the subjects of its examination in time, correspondingly. The navigation and the interface are developed mainly by means of typography and dynamic means of plastic arts. The page layout is visualized mainly by means of graphic design, whereas a set of pages is harmonized in the montage (Figure 4).

The foundation for the design of any message is its thought. Thought is formulated at the strategic level in

Figure 5. Drawing parallels between the level of strategy and the level of concept.

the informational/programmatically organization. In parallel with the level of strategy, we are positioning the level of concept for the compositional organization of multimedia presentations. Design concept formulated as 'the central artistic project idea' is accompanied by the strategies, which are able to empower a technical development of the project (Figure 5).

Textual and visual documental materials serve as building blocks for the construction of an artistic space. Software features are the building blocks for the construction of an interactive time frame through the elemental content of the composition. Multimedia presentation is constructed from the variously assorted sources of information. The information comes as text, images, sounds, and software features. If one draws a parallel between the level of scope and the level of the elemental content of the composition, one can see the following: data on the informational/programmatically side are only a speculative list of illustrations and references to the relevant sections, whereas on the composite side these data are transformed into a tangible stack of images that the viewer can sort interactively, for example, through pushing one from the other (Figure 6).

Information architecture is visualized in the virtual space. The interaction scenarios are visualized in the multivariate hypertext storylines. Creating a virtual space and the options for interaction with it can be compared with the development of a story and a plot, say for a film or a novel. A story is a set of information units systematically placed in the space-time continuum, whereas a plot is the rigid sequence in which the user (reader, viewer, spectator) gets these units. Organization of the virtual space is comparable to the organization of the exhibition where the network of the node pages is an accomplished module, each page being a separate collection of 'artefacts' associated with the whole system of organization, naming, and navigation.

Unlike the masterpieces of an exhibition existing in a real environment, the information of multimedia presentation is distributed in the virtual space. We consider the system of information blocks associated by harmonic relationships as a virtual three-dimensional composition level of an edition. This level of composition is characterized by the fact that it cannot be seen instantly, but instead it can be presented through the interactive sorting of its parts, and its echoes on the surface of the screen. This level can be seen instantly only with the means of

2. Level of scope

2. Level of compositional elements

```
//var imagePath1 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_SCU_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.JPG';
var imagePath1 = '/uploadedimages/sqg_logo_pixel_rca_026.jpg';
var imagePath2 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_SCU_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.JPG';
var imagePath3 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_GSM_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.jpg';
var imagePath4 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_IRabbitpunch.flv.jpg';
var imagePath5 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_TEX_PRO-09_1.jpg';
var imagePath6 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_COLL_ofili.jpg';
var imagePath7 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_WOM_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.JPG';
var imagePath8 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_apple-iphone-in-hand-thumb.jpg';
var imagePath9 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_MEN_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.JPG';
var imagePath10 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_HIS_PRO-09_2.jpg';
var imagePath11 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_TongueSucker.jpg';
var imagePath12 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_sustain_logo.jpg';
var imagePath13 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_animation2.jpg';
var imagePath14 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_FSS_alys.tomlinson_02.jpg';
var imagePath15 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_dl_silhouettes1.jpg';
var imagePath16 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_EXH_ShowRCA_01.jpg';
var imagePath17 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_COM_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.jpg';
var imagePath18 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_CarbonHero2.JPG';
var imagePath19 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_tony_pic_5.jpg';
var imagePath20 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_Dominic_2.jpg';
var imagePath21 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_Tord-Portrait.jpg';
var imagePath22 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_STORY_Schaffner_PRO-09_Ekua_McMorris.JPG';
var imagePath23 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_GSM_ALUMNI_Karola.jpg';
var imagePath24 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_ABOUT_Pro-09_Soraya.jpg';
var imagePath25 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_ABOUT_Environment.jpg';
var imagePath26 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_PAN_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.JPG';
var imagePath27 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_Inside Outside Inside_3.jpg';
var imagePath28 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_PRO_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.jpg';
var imagePath29 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_ALUMNI_Dyson_seatruck.jpg';
var imagePath30 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_night_show.jpg';
var imagePath31 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_ABOUT_tomlinson_PRO-09_8.jpg';
var imagePath32 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_BAT_corner main view2.jpg';
var imagePath33 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_inan01.flv.jpg';
var imagePath34 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_ro_cassiboy.JPG';
var imagePath35 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_CER_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.JPG';
var imagePath36 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_DSC4057.jpg';
var imagePath14 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_FSS_alys.tomlinson_02.jpg';
var imagePath15 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_dl_silhouettes1.jpg';
var imagePath16 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_EXH_ShowRCA_01.jpg';
var imagePath17 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_COM_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.jpg';
```


Ceramics & Glass

Figure 6. Drawing parallels between the level of scope and the level of compositional elements.

3. Level of structure

3. Level of three-dimensional organization

Figure 7. Drawing parallels between the level of structure and the level of three-dimensional organization.

simulation. As an example, a colour-graphical model of the three-dimensional level of the website of Domus Academy (2011), in comparison with its hypertext structure, is shown in Figure 7.

Navigation systems provide orientation in the virtual space. They are most often expressed visually in the colour palette coding and labelling pages or the typography. Movement through the virtual space is provided by the interface. Interface elements are

expressed by the typographical release, e.g., by an explicit graphical isolation of the areas from the content, or by the form changes, which are dictated by an event. The interface shows the navigation through the formatting: links are encoded with the appropriate colour section; some complex elements (e.g., the drop-down lists) display the structure in a minimized form. Modification of an interface creates different types of intra-movement: moving, panning, dragging, zooming, etc. Visual organization of the navigation and

4. Level of navigation and interface

MASTER PROGRAMS

- Accessories Design
- Business Design
- Car Design
- Design
- Fashion Design
- Fashion Management
- Interaction Design
- Interior and Living Design
- Service and Experience Design
- Urban Vision and Architectural Design

4. Level of spatio-temporal organization

Figure 8. Drawing parallels between the level of navigation and interface and the level of spatio-temporal organization.

5. Level of layout

5. Level of flat organization

Figure 9. Drawing parallels between the level of layout and the level of flat organization.

the interface forms a spatio-temporal composition level of the multimedia presentation (Figure 8).

Visualized by means of graphic design, pages are mapped to the time by means of cinematography (through montage). Apart from a presentation, any page is a whole composition. Usually the identification zone acts as a dominant, as opposed to the content zone. Graphically accented interface elements serve as the echoes of it. Grouping the items, as well as the textual and illustrative areas, rhythmically organizes the movement at a glance of the page. The movement is supported by the dynamics of a disclosure of interface elements.

On the surface of the screen it is crucial to identify the information in relation to the virtual organization (three-dimensional or volume-spatial composition level) of the multimedia presentations, because its holistic interpretation is possible only in the space-time mapping of the parts handled on the plane. In each page, on each plane, the representation of virtual forms of presentation is combined with the forms of interaction with virtuality itself, as well as with the forms of meaningful information. The plane of the screen harmonizes the elements of the organization at all levels, creating a flat composition level (Figure 9).

We have found that the two-dimensionality of the multidimensional expressions of the virtual space on

the planar screen causes mutual interdependence of the elements and the means of three-dimensional and two-dimensional composition. It thus suggests their connection through the elements and through the spatio-temporal composition that occur when deploying an interactive presentation in spatio-temporal space.

Thus, the projection of artistic means of expression at the informational/programmatic organization of the site allowed us to identify the levels of organization of the composite multimedia presentation: (1) the level of concept, (2) the level of the compositional elements, (3) the three-dimensional compositional level, (4) the spatio-temporal level of composition, and (5) the flat compositional level. The scheme of compositional organization is shown in Figure 10.

Conclusions

A multimedia presentation is a form of social communication, which has both an information and a communication function. A message is perceived by the person both rationally and emotionally, necessitating both logical and imaginative formation. Combining the logical and the imaginative structures is implemented in the synthesis of informational/programmatic and compositional organization of multimedia presentations.

Logical organization of the forms of multimedia presentation includes information and software aspects. A scheme of informational/programmatic organization includes (1) the level of strategy, (2) the level of scope, (3) the level of hypertext structure, (4) the level of navigation and interface, and (5) the layout level.

A visual, or shaped, organization of the form of multimedia presentation is carried out both in space and in time. The elements of this form are structured in a virtual environment, forming a three-dimensional composition. Space unfolds on the pages of the edition in the spatio-temporal composition, whereas each page is organized as a planar composition.

A compositional organization of the forms of multimedia presentation comprises (1) the level of concept, (2) the level of compositional elements, (3) the three-dimensional compositional level, (4) the spatio-temporal compositional level, and (5) the flat compositional level. An artistic form of a multimedia presentation is created as a holistic integration of a three-dimensional, spatio-temporal and in-plane composition.

To conclude, we adjusted the Garrett web design model to apply it to the case of multimedia presentation by adding an emotional component on each level. Thus, we supplemented the 'Elements of User Experience' by the 'Elements of Viewer Experience'. Today we are faced with the fact that the user experience has become a central focus for the usability of technology (McCarthy & Wright, 2004). Consequently, users of interactive technologies are now considered as complex, emotional experiencers (Mattelmäki, 2006). Based on our own experience, we

Figure 10. Compositional organization.

analysed the human expectations both from the user and viewer standpoints, and created the ways that help deliver better design solutions.

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Want to speak? Envisioning driver-to-driver communication for emotion regulation

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Abstract Poor communication between car drivers elicits negative emotion while driving. In this study, we envisioned rich communication between drivers to alleviate their negative emotions. An empirical study was conducted based on the conceptual design prototype for emoticon-based communication between car drivers. We found key findings and insights for enriching driver-to-driver communication for emotion regulation. The results were categorized into three aspects: driver-to-driver communication as rich communication, social communication and computer-mediated communication.

Keywords Driver interaction, Emotion regulation, Interpersonal communication, User experience

Introduction

The term “aggressive drivers” was identified for the first time by Tillman and Hobbs (Tillman & Hobbs, 1949). Even though it was almost 70 years ago, aggressive driving (“road rage”) is still a current social issue. Several studies have shown the relationship between the negative emotion of car drivers and its impact for poor driving performance. Bañuls and Montoro (Bañuls & Montoro, 2001) mentioned that drivers who are confused have a high possibility of breaking traffic rules, which can lead to accidents. Hudlicka and McNeese (Hudlicka & Mcneese, 2002) found that nervousness of drivers can cause them to focus on specific sights too much or make biased judgments. Various studies including Wells-Parker et al. (Wells-Parker et al., 2002) have reported that anger of drivers can increase the car crash rate. For these reasons, it is important to solve the emotional problems of drivers.

There were several approaches to focusing on the emotion of drivers. Jonsson et al. (Jonsson et al., 2004) explored the effect of blaming drivers with recorded voice on their attitudes. Nass et al. (Nass et al., 2005) examined the impact of matching the car voice emotion and the driver emotion. Harris and Nass (Harris & Nass, 2011) proposed the auditory interface to regulate the emotion of drivers with the psychological background. Although much work has been done, it is necessary to define which emotional situation or context while driving is important.

Driving on the road is a social activity wherein drivers continually influence each other. One of the important factors that cause drivers to develop negative emotions is poor communication with other drivers (Shinar, 1998). Current communication channels while driving such as horn, turn signals and high beam are restricted modalities because of the cognitive workload and visual distraction of drivers. Due to these safety issues, drivers only can communicate

with a limited amount of information.

However, after 100 years of history in the automobile industry, cars are now changing from mechanical products to electronic products, with the development of ubiquitous computing, internet-of-things (IOT) services and vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) technology. With these technological backgrounds, drivers can be allowed to exchange the amount of information with other drivers. Moreover, automation issues such as driver assistance systems may solve current restriction of communication modalities.

Recent studies explored the possibility of driver-to-driver communication. Schroeter et al. (Schroeter et al., 2012) mentioned the concept scenarios of the vehicle as a social platform. Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2014) suggested scenarios for driver-to-driver communication on the highway made by a design workshop. Lamas et al. (Lamas et al., 2014) conducted scenario-based study with 24 participants and found requirements and design issues for driver-to-driver communication. Liu et al. (Liu et al., 2015) examined the effect of expressing emotion while driving with emoticons and simple text. Although much work has been done, in-situ studies need to be conducted to explore the possibility of a new way of communication between drivers, especially focusing on emotion regulation.

In the study, we designed the conceptual design prototype for emoticon-based communication between car drivers and found its value via an empirical study. The purpose of the study is to conduct qualitative in-the-wild user study to observe and analyze user experience in driver-to-driver communication context. The first contribution of the study is to explore what considerations or factors are important to design driver-to-driver communication for emotion regulation. The second contribution is to provide a new design opportunity for interaction designers and

Figure 1. Vision in Product Design (ViP) model and envisioning driver-to-driver communication for emotion regulation.

researchers to help them envision driver-to-driver communication for emotion regulation in the near future.

Envisioning driver-to-driver communication for emotion regulation

The process of the study follows the Vision in Product Design (ViP) model by Hekkert and Van Dijk (Hekkert & Van Dijk, 2001) to systematize our approach to driver-to-driver communication for emotion regulation (Figure 1). As we mentioned in the introduction part, we started the old product (WHAT): the current communication modality or device between drivers. The problem is mainly focused on interaction level (HOW): poor communication can result from ambiguity or possibility of misunderstanding. This problem is an important issue in the driving context because it can have a negative impact on the emotion of drivers and their safety (WHY). The study envisions the future context wherein the drivers can alleviate their negative emotions that are occurring because of communication between drivers (WHY). We conducted

the study through the design artifact, which was designed for emoticon-based communication (HOW) and explored the experience of drivers. These steps might assist in designing a new communication system between drivers that will help regulate their emotions (WHAT).

System design

We suggest the system design of driver-to-driver communication for emotion regulation based on the communication model of Shannon (Shannon, 2001) (Figure 2). It consists of five features: Speaker (Source), Encoder, Channel, Decoder, and Listener (Receiver). The driver who wants to speak (Speaker) sends the message to other drivers. Encoding and decoding is assisted by the Channel, such as wireless V2V technology. Then, the other driver (Listener) receives the message. We thought this process could prompt two changes for drivers: affective change and behavioral change. Speaker may reduce the negative emotion by speaking some emotion aloud or giving other information to the Listener. The Listener may

Figure 2. System design of driver-to-driver communication for emotion regulation.

Figure 3. The process model of emotion regulation. Examples were from Quoidbach et al. (Quoidbach et al., 2015).

reduce the negative emotion by listening to some words from the Speaker. Behavioral change can be performed by both drivers while certain events occur on the road. Based on the rich communication, we expect that the Speaker and Listener can control their emotions through the communication and can change their driving behavior in a positive way.

In this study, we started from these questions: If we let drivers use the design artifact that enables drivers to do rich communication with other drivers, what kinds of emotion or information will the drivers want to speak (listen) and why? What kinds of context will they want to speak (listen)? What is the relationship between their communicating behavior and their emotion?

Emotion regulation

The process model of emotion regulation is based on the Gross's work (Gross, 1998). The model suggests that emotions might be regulated at one of five points: 1) Selection of the situation, 2) Modification of the situation, 3) Deployment of attention, 4) Change of cognitions, and 5) Modulation of the response. We envision the system which can regulate the driver's emotion based on these five points. As a starting point, we implemented the prototype which is focused on the 4) Change of cognitions and 5) Modulation of the response. The prototype allows the emotional expressions to other drivers via emoticons and we hope the prototype may elicit the driver's cognitive change and the user's modulation of the response.

Method

Online survey

We conducted an online survey to obtain diverse opinions and objective data from drivers. The survey was carried out online to enhance respondent accessibility, and a survey supplied by Google Spreadsheets was used. A total of 75 cases were collected among 51 males and 24 females. We provided questions regarding 1) the level of stress felt when driving, 2) the need for communication between other drivers while driving, 3) which emotion is expressed most to other drivers when driving, 4) how to express information or emotions to other drivers.

The result of the online survey shows that Ninety-two percent of respondents (69 in total) felt stress during driving. Of all respondents, 84.3% (64 total) answered that they needed to communicate with other drives while they drove, which shows that most drivers need communication with other drivers. The most expressed emotions from driver to driver were appreciation (24 instances), anger (17 instances), regret/apology (16 instances), and surprise (9 instances). The reported means to convey information or emotions to other drivers were using the turn signal on both side (20 instances), using high beams (18 instance), honking the horn (16 instances), using hand signals (10 instances), using facial expressions (3 instances), using voice (2 instances), and holding down the head (2 instances).

Design artifact

Based on the survey results, we designed the prototype which allows the emotional expressions to other drivers via emoticons (Figure 3). A driver could express the four different emotions with the prototype: appreciation (happy), anger, apology (crying) and surprise. It was designed for use in a real driving context rather than a simulator.

The prototype consists of four main buttons that were installed on the center console (middle of the dashboard) and a red LED dot matrix on the rear window (Figure 4). When the driver presses a button, the emoticon is shown on an LED display, and the driver who follows can recognize it. We considered the usability of a driver who presses the button, considering distraction and safety issues. The color and the size of the emoticon also were considered carefully to clearly identify the emotional expression to the following driver. The prototype was implemented by Arduino to control the LED display output with input buttons.

Experimental design

Ten drivers participated in the study. The average age of the participants was 27 years old (ranging from 24 to 36, SD = 3.32). All participants had more than one year of driving experience, considering the safety issue of in-the-wild study. The participants drove a car that was rented from a car-sharing service, and the prototype was installed. Another participant drove in

Figure 4. Design sketches for driver-to-driver communication.

Figure 5. Design artifact: emoticon buttons (left) and LED display on the rear window (right).

another car and followed the car in which prototype was installed. Every participant made a pair, and they took part in two different driving sessions to experience both 1) expressing emotion to the driver following behind and 2) understanding the emotion of the front driver. We also implemented a normal driving session (driving without prototype) to compare the driver's attention and attitude in both condition. Therefore, there were four different driving sessions in the experiment (Figure 5). To control the four different conditions, we fixed the driving route. The driving route was designed to take around 10 minutes, or a total of 40 minutes, for one participant. The route included narrow roads, high levels of pedestrian movement, and numerous traffic lights. We focused on what participants felt about the driving experience across the four different conditions. Due to safety issues, a researcher of the experiment sat next to the driver in every session, and we recorded 1) the behavior and speaking of the driver and 2) the front view while driving. The researcher asked the driver to speak out loud about interesting events related to other drivers, not only when the driver pushed the buttons. After the participants finished driving, the participants came back to the laboratory and were interviewed. In the interview, we asked for the participants' opinions about the driving experience,

and the video that recorded the driving session was played during the interview so that participants could easily recall the situation.

Results & discussion

We analyzed and evaluated the data that we recorded during the driving sessions and the debriefing interview. There were several findings and insights to consider while assessing the design of the driver-to-driver communication system and its relation to emotion. We summarized and categorized the results into three different perspectives of communication.

Figure 6. Experimental design: driving sessions.

Rich communication

According to the interview, most participants positively mentioned the richness of the communication between drivers. The comments were about the new value and possibility of the communication system. They mentioned that communication via emoticon was easy and fun. Moreover, they agreed that the device may elicit a positive atmosphere between drivers. The important insight about the richness of the communication is that participants have used the prototype for two objectives: 1) to deliver information related to driving context and 2) to express their own feeling and emotion directly to others.

Delivering rich information

Some of the participants used the prototype to deliver more information that they only could send through the prototype. It was an interesting finding because we designed the prototype to let the user to only convey their own emotion or feeling. In the case of P2, the participant delivered the driving situation cue through the emoticon. P7 tried to elicit the empathy of the driver rather than express an emotion itself.

“Traffic information also can be transmitted by emotional expression. For example, when the pedestrians block the narrow alley, I can show the ‘crying’ emoticon and let the driver behind know that I’m also stuck.” (P2)

“When the car in front of me drives too slowly or the red [stop] light was too long, I pressed the crying button to elicit the empathy of the driver behind me.” (P7)

Expressing & understanding feeling

Compared to the previous examples, the expression of emotion was also useful to alleviate participants’ feelings such as anger. We found that the prototype enables drivers to express emotion as they tell a story to other people in terms of controlling their own emotion or making empathy.

“When I was angry, I expressed the anger with the ‘anger’ emoticon to the driver behind me rather than honking to the front. And the anger eased a little bit.” (P2)

“By pressing the several emoticons, I delivered my feeling as if to tell the driver behind me.” (P3)

Social communication

Social distance

The current communication system between drivers is based on anonymity and the physical shield among drivers (Ellison - Potter et al., 2001). If the rich driver-to-driver communication does not fully consider the social distance between drivers, it might have a negative impact on the driving experience. We found the possibility of the communication system maintaining the social distance in a gentle way and enabling the emotional empathy between the drivers at the same time. It is a valuable insight that the communication can move beyond the signal sending

and receiving.

“... [When I saw the emoticon] I could have a good impression of the front driver. Then, I was thinking about why the driver presses that [emoticon] button, and I tried to feel empathy the driver.” (P3)

“I pressed the crying button, and I expect that the driver behind me can alleviate [a] stuffy feeling. If all drivers can communicate like this, polite and considerate driving can be possible.” (P7)

“When I see the smiling face [emoticon], I also smiled as if I was facing the other person who smiles.” (P8)

Personality

We found that the driver’s personality may affect the rich communication and that designers should consider the various kinds of drivers. This is an important finding because the strategy for emotion regulation also should be different depending on drivers. The system may help some drivers who are not familiar to express their emotion to other drivers, as P1 said.

“...When driving alone, I do not make much expression to other drivers, but these kinds of options might allow easier emotional expression, even if the driver is passive.” (P1)

Computer-mediated communication

Current driver-to-driver communication has different characteristics from face-to-face communication, which is more verbal and has eye-contact. Renner and Johansson (Renner & Johansson, 2006) and Lamas et al. (Lamas et al., 2014) also mentioned the difference between driver-to-driver communication and face-to-face interaction. Moreover, we found that it is necessary to compare the characteristics of driver-to-driver communication with computer-mediated communication (CMC) (Walther, 1996). Computer-mediated communication such as text messaging and online chat has similar characteristics to rich driver-to-driver communication because some medium between users exists and should be designed precisely. To develop the rich communication between drivers, mediating drivers based on the characteristics of driver-to-driver communication is essential.

Modality

Several comments about modality or functional issue were collected. P3 recommended the voice or speech-based communication. However, there was concern about the modality because it can bother the driver while he or she is listening to other content, especially when a voiced navigation system is turned on. Not only the issue of social distance but also the sound or voice should be precisely intended and designed. Other functional details included the need for clear feedback when the driver sends the message to others (P6) or a function allowing a driver behind to send a message to a driver in front (P7).

Trust

Although we studied rich communication, a misunderstanding also can occur. In the experiment,

we found that emoticon is also ambiguous in complex driving context. If the rich communication is the same as a phone call or so-called “walkie-talkie,” expression of anger or negative emotion can directly lead to danger. This suggests the importance of encoding and decoding process through the channel, which is a matter of how the designer designs the medium between drivers. If the expression of the drivers can be revised, reduced, or even exaggerated to elicit positive atmosphere between drivers, it might connect to the trust issue: trust between drivers, and trust between the driver and the car interface. How much of this should the designers control? What is the optimal system for driver-to-driver communication and emotion regulation as a new type of computer-mediated communication?

Limitation

The customs and etiquettes related to car driving are different in various cultures. However, our study was only conducted in South Korea. Cultural issues related to driver-to-driver communication should be further investigated across various cultures. Moreover, our study was an in-the-wild study, and the safety of the drivers was important. Thus, a researcher sat next to the participants in every observation, but this might have caused Hawthorne effect. We should try to find a better way to observe the driver when they are driving alone, because emotional expression and communication between drivers can be affected by the other passenger.

Conclusion

We studied how drivers can communicate with other drivers through a conceptual design artifact. The prototype enabled the participants to communicate rich information and convey emotion via emoticon. The participants generally accepted the prototype positively, and we found key findings and insights related to enriching driver-to-driver communication for emotion regulation. In conclusion, the emotion-expressing interface can provide additional values, including new and positive driving experiences for drivers. For future work, making a design artifact for speech-based communication and trying to mount an empirical study with quantitative measure would be valuable. Moreover, we should consider the driver-to-driver communication strategies for emotion regulation of drivers based on psychological background. Based on the findings and insights in this study, we will focus on making a framework for designing driver-to-driver communication involving emotion regulation.

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“I need that data”: Exploring the data experience of amateur runners

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Abstract Running is an affordable way of becoming physically active. Currently, amateur runners utilize running trackers to keep records of their training and be aware of their performance. These special type of users experience “data” in addition to the running trackers. While there are studies that examine the experience of physical activity trackers, there is no study that explore the data experience of runners. Thus, this paper explores the dimensions of data experience of amateur runners who employ running trackers to learn about their performance. By giving a brief review of literature, this paper demonstrates how amateur runners experience data and how they expect to be informed, through a qualitative study conducted with 30 amateur runners. The paper will end with design suggestions to support the design of future running trackers that better meet amateur runners’ data needs.

Keywords *User experience, Running trackers, Amateur runners, Data experience*

Background of the study

Motivating people to be physically active has been the focus of a great number of studies in the last five years. Mainly, these studies focused on making people aware of themselves, by giving personal information (i.e., their physical activity performance) and motivate them to have better behavior (i.e. to get active). Meanwhile researchers have explored the ways in which people interact with physical activity trackers and how they persuade people to change their behavior positively (Kuru & Forlizzi, 2015). While early research explored aesthetic qualities and game-like visualizations of activity data to motivate people (Arteaga, Kudeki, Woodworth, & Kurniawan, 2010; Consolvo, Everitt, Smith, & Landay, 2006; Consolvo, Klasnja, et al., 2008; Consolvo, McDonald, et al., 2008; Fujiki et al., 2008; Lin, Mamykina, Lindtner, Delojoux, & Strub, 2006; Nelson, Megens, & Peeters, 2012); others focused on the social and motivational aspects of sharing data (Ahtinen et al., 2008; Fialho et al., 2009); and suggested personalization of product appearance (Edwards, McDonald, Zhao, & Humphries, 2013) or the data (Consolvo, McDonald, et al., 2008). Not surprisingly, currently there are several physical activity trackers in the market and people utilize these devices to make healthy decisions. Mainly, these trackers encourage people to take at least 10K steps a day which is perceived to be a good way of staying healthy. This is what make these special class of products serve as persuasive and informative tools, aiming at helping people to “collect and reflect personal information” (Li, Dey, & Forlizzi, 2010).

When people realize that they can walk long distances, running becomes an alternative way of going further and faster. A new type of users emerge as a result of this shift. That is “amateur runners” who expect to learn about their speed, the distance they run or the total calories they burn while running. In time,

counting the number of steps taken becomes an insufficient way of witnessing the improvement in self performance. Thus, the personal data is seen as one of the best ways to understand the runner’s personal improvement. That is the reason why people tend to use several applications or sports watches to track their running activity. As a result, designing tracking technology for outdoor activities, especially for running is on the rise. While companies like Garmin and Suunto develop activity trackers for outdoor running, understanding needs of amateur runners requires special interest.

Research in running trackers is new relative to research in physical activity trackers. Currently, studies explore how amateur runners experience GPS-based running trackers (Bauer, 2013; Bauer & Kratschmar, 2015; Jennings, Cormack, Coutts, Boyd, & Aughey, 2010; Jensen & Mueller, 2014; Shipway & Jones, 2007; Wozniak, Knaving, Björk, & Fjeld, 2015). For instance, in a recent research, it is suggested that these products should have a special training feature to empower the technique of runners (Jensen & Mueller, 2014). Another research focuses on “social understanding of runners” to find out how technology can help runners during races (Wozniak, Knaving, Björk, & Fjeld, 2015). Thinking that the most important benefit of using running tracker is learning about self, understanding the runners’ experience with trackers is essential to further explore the “data experience” of amateur runners. However, while there are lots of studies that assert explain user experience of technological products, the literature lacks an overview of the runners’ experience with the personal data. Thus this contribution can lead the developers and interaction designers to put forward the users’ data requirements from running trackers to design for better running experience. In this sense, focusing on the runners’ data experience has the potential to lead

designers to understand how to design running trackers and better deliver user data to the amateur runners; to engage runners with the personal data interrupting the flow of running experience.

Meanwhile literature evolved from focusing on usability to user experience, the definition of user experience also evolved. Alben described the user experience of interactive products as a holistic set of factors, including how people feel about a product, how well they understand its functions, how the product makes people feel when using it, and how it fits its purpose and context of its use (1996). A later work posed user experience in interaction design as the interaction between product and user, unfolding in a social and cultural context of use (Forlizzi & Ford, 2000; Hassenzahl, 2003). The experience of interacting with a technology is dynamic, and is affected by many factors, including time, place, goals, emotion, behavior, attitudes, and expectations, and other people. Additionally, people's expectations change with new technology, because new functions and features need to be made sense of and need to be taken into account relative to goals in product use (Hassenzahl, 2008; Nurkka, Kujala, & Kempainen, 2009; Stelmaszewska, Fields, & Blandford, 2004).

With this regard, in this paper, a new term "data experience" is defined as the ability to inspire and motivate runners, allowing repeated interaction with personal data over time. With this focus, this paper puts forward the details and dimensions of data experience of runners. Details of data experience will be explained in the following lines, with the initial findings of an exploratory study of tracking experience of amateur runners.

Methodology

To understand the dimensions and components of data experience, a qualitative research was conducted by asking 30 amateur runners. The participants were interviewed, and structured analysis was made to find the details of their experience.

Selection of participants

The study was intended to include amateur runners who had been actively running, had attended at least one national race, and had been using technology to track the details of their running performance. The participants were recruited through email, phone or word of mouth. They were invited to participate in the study and after the interview, they were asked whether they knew any other runners who would help in the study.

Data collection

The study was designed as semi-structured interviews. Interviews covered detailed questions about participants' experience with the running trackers and especially their data experience. Their needs and expectations were also asked which would maintain their engagement with the data. The questioned covered: (1) what were their data-related needs that made them use a tracking technology; (2) what kind of data they needed during running and why; (3) what other data-related expectations would

lead them to change the product they use. The face to face interviews were conducted mutually agreed time and place. All the interviews were voice recorded with permission. The study did not require any other special setting.

Participants

In total 30 amateur runners (14 female and 16 male whose age ranged from 21 to 40) were selected for the study in accordance with the personal judgments about who may contribute to the study. Of the participants, 21 were using a smart watch to track their experience while 9 was using a mobile app (Table 1). When asked in detail, of the participants 24 had used a mobile app before the current tracker they used; 4 had used a sports watch and 2 had used nothing. Not surprisingly, those who had been using a sports watch to track their training had previously used either a mobile app or another entry level GPS based sports watch. Among the participants, 5 had been training less than one year on regular basis, 15 had been training for one to three years, and 10 had been training more than four years.

Analysis and results

In order to avoid the reductivity of data (Blomberg & Burrell, 2008; Diggins & Tolmie, 2003), data was analyzed by applying Content Analysis (Krippendorff, 2004). Each voice record was transcribed into Excel sheets. Then, open coding was conducted to identify data related needs and expectations of participants (Strauss & Corbin, 1990). During the coding process, to maintain the consistency, the first coding was done only by the interviewer. For assessing reliability of the coding (Krippendorff, 2004), another researcher went through the codes. An iterative process was carried out until an agreement was reached.

Using the explained analysis technique, 623 data related comments were listed. In total 5 main dimensions were defined with 27 type of running related data. The qualitative analysis technique enabled understanding the relations between dimensions of data experience and type of data that is

Table 1. The Apps and the Sports Watches that Participants Used.

	Tracker being used	# of participants
App Users	Endomondo	3
	Nike Plus	3
	RunKeeper	1
	Strava	2
Watch Users	Garmin Forerunner 220	9
	Garmin Forerunner 910XT	3
	Nike Sports Watch	3
	Garmin Forerunner 25	1
	Garmin Fenix2	1
	Garmin Fenix3	1
	Suunto Ambit 3	1
	Suunto Ambit 2	1
		1
	TOTAL	30

Figure 1. Relations between the Components of Data Experience.

related with that experience. Incorporating the relations between those will lead to learn the dynamics of data experience of runners. To do this, the number of comments were used to create the graph of relations. For this, "NodeXL (Smith et al., 2009) network graphs creating software was used. The outcome graph is aimed to understand the emphasis of relations and to figure out the potentials of further research. In this graph, the sizes of the circles indicate the strength of the dimension or type of data in comparison to others. Besides, the strength of the lines indicates the strength of the relation between the quality and the characteristic. The distance between the circles does not have any significant meaning (Figure 1).

It was realized that runners' data experience were mainly under five main dimensions: *usefulness*, *interactivity*, *personalization*, *connectivity* and *accuracy*. As expected, participants talked about the usefulness of data more than other qualities of data in their experience. They talked about the type of data they need and reasons behind those. Second, they talked about interactivity of data which was declared to be an important quality in their data experience. Third, they talked about the personalization of data; how the data talks about the user and how it should further be personalized. They also talked about the data connectivity and accuracy, as these also define the way they know about self.

The Figure1 illustrates that, *heart rate*, *pace*, *distance*, *GPS*, *elevation gain*, *instant pace* and *time elapsed* are the most important data that runners care most. The data showed that all participants (n=30) talked about heart rate, pace (or speed), distance and time while they talked about their data experience. On the other hand, lap data (n=13), elevation gain (n=12) and

training history (n=12) were also mentioned by the participants by relating these types of data with the dimensions listed above. In the following lines, the details of the dimensions will be discussed.

Usefulness of data

The first dimension of data experience is usefulness, that can be defined as the "system's ability to inform the user with the required data before, during and after running".

Data from the study revealed that runners care about usefulness of the *heart rate*, *pace*, *distance* and *cadence* data as well as the overall *historical* summary of these. It was stated that, *heart rate* is the most important data, as it indicates whether the runner is training within the limits of "safe-zone" or not. That is, when the heart rate is too high, it may be the indicator of heart problems. Amateur runners use their *pace* data mostly during running to assess whether their heart is in safe as it was stated to be one of the most important indicators of effort level. It is also stated to be an indicator of "healthy run". Following that, amateur runners would like to reach the *history* of their runs, to be able to compare their performance with the previous runs. This also is required to understand whether their performance is improving or not. *Distance* and *pace* data are mostly used during running. Obviously amateur runners would like to know about the distance and speed they run, and to decide at which kilometer they would stop running. Interestingly, participants mentioned about the usefulness of *cadence*, the number of steps taken per minute. Those who talked about the usefulness of cadence data, would like to keep their cadence at a certain level to avoid the injuries.

Elevation gain data was mostly mentioned by the participants who train for trail races. For those participants, it was stated to be more important than pace data as their pace can change when they go up hills and they mostly don't care what their pace was in a run, but the elevation gain. Finally, *time elapsed* was stated to be important by a few number of participants. It was because, when the runner knows about the distance and pace, how much time elapsed can be guessed.

Interactivity

The second dimension of data experience is interactivity, means "the system's ability to communicate with the user, who expects to connect to the system whenever they desire."

Data from the study revealed that runners care about interactivity of their *pace*, *distance*, *heart rate*, *elevation gain* and *instant pace* data mostly. It was stated that, interactivity of *pace*, *distance* and *heart rate* are required during running, in order the runners to instantly check the details of their run. As these three types of data are stated to be the indicators of "safe-zone" running, they are expected to be interacted smoothly and directly when needed. As the trail run lovers care *elevation gain* data, it was stated that interactivity of elevation gain data during running is critical for them, especially when they train for special races that has high elevation gain. Finally, importance of interactivity of *instant pace* was stated mostly by road runners as they define their race pace by comparing their instant pace with their target race pace during running. Mainly knowing instant pace helps the runner avoid going too fast or too slow during running.

Personalization

The third characteristic is personalization, which can be defined as "the system's ability to allow the user to make changes in the information content" to best support individuals' needs.

In the study, it was discovered that runners wanted the system to "talk to" them specifically, rather than just collecting data and analyzing it according to pre-defined parameters. They wished the system to make suggestions for their training by analyzing their data, and expected the system to adapt itself to its users in relation to their changing needs and goals. The participants described how personalization is important for interactive systems, because personalized information strengthens the feeling of ownership of the system and inspires extended use. In addition, participants expected the trackers to allow them to personalize the interaction with the data. They expected to see their *pace* and *heart rate* instantly during running. Therefore, while talking about the user specifically, the system should allow the user to personalize the interaction so that the runners can reach the type of data they need.

Connectivity

The fourth dimension is connectivity, which is defined as "the system's ability to connect with other media to be able to make correct calculations."

Connectivity is important in order to engage the runner with the tracker frequently to make meaningful interpretations about one's self. Through adaptive technology, instant data access should be ensured to enable runners analyze their personal data immediately, and take instant steps to overcome the unexpected results. For instance, checking data instantly and seeing the instant pace correctly can result in taking action to avoid any injuries. On the other hand, participants stated that some of the systems lack instant GPS connection which results in lack in accuracy of some of the data.

Accuracy

The final characteristic is accuracy, which is defined as "the system's ability to collect and show data correctly."

All participants expected the systems to give accurate data. Accuracy in the data measurement identifies the level of people's reliance on the system. It is also influential of usefulness and interactivity data. Accuracy comes into prominence as runners expect the system to "talk about them specifically". Lack in accuracy of the data results in a barrier to keep using the system. This is because, people think that there is no sense to continue using a "useless" system. In relation to the previous findings, results indicated that runners care for the accuracy of instant pace and GPS-connection. In some models of sports watches, even though it has high importance, the *instant pace* data is not accurate enough for them to track it. It is because, the GPS connection is not accurate enough to track the runner live.

Implications for design

In this paper, five dimensions of data experience has been presented which were derived from a semi structured study conducted with 30 amateur runners. Trackers that are designed to support these dimensions will likely to offer holistic and engaging data experience. While each dimension can serve as a mechanism for creating rich experience for different types of trackers, these five dimensions can also work together to sustain long term experience for single set of system for all amateur runners.

Products and systems can offer features that are adaptive to runners' changing goals. They can also take individual differences, such as general wellness, injury, and illness, into consideration. The feedback that the tracker presents should be designed in a motivating manner and be presented in real time. To design an interactive running tracker that offer rich data experience in relation to the five characteristics, designers should consider the following:

1) *Connectivity is a requirement, as it keeps people trust in personal data.* The interactive running tracker must offer several simple and direct ways to access data, and data access should transfer seamlessly between access points. Current Bluetooth or wireless technologies can be utilized to satisfy the needs of the runners. It should also react according to a runners' changing contexts of use. For instance, when the runner travels to another city or country, it should not

need any adjustment to connect to the GPS. There should also be no delay in connecting to the system and accessing one's data by sustaining accuracy of data. This requirement is extremely essential for runners as instant and accurate data access is a means for runners to trust in both the system and personal data.

2) *Data visualizations and interaction with data should be designed to support usefulness and interactivity of data.* Here the aim is to keep runners' interest in learning from the tracker and be curious about "what comes next". For example, the system should offer a number of ways to present and make meaning from the data. During running, it obviously should give the details of the run that the runner requires. So it would be easy for the user to understand where he or she is relative to a goal, if there is one. It can also make suggestions during running if the runner is behind a predefined goal. As stated, heart rate is the most important data, which indicates whether the runner is training within the limits of "safe-zone" or not. The tracker should be extremely careful in presenting the heart rate data to the runner in order not to cause irrelevant disturbance. Presenting data in real-time and accurate also keeps runners motivated and curious about the momentary data.

3) *Personalized information and interactions offer more engaging data experience.* As discussed, a tracker that delivers personalized information will empower the runner to take action immediately. Prompts or incentives that have been tailored to an individual keep runner motivated to work towards their goals. Other forms of personalized interactions can include incentives or inspirational information. A design for personalization is not static; it needs to be tailored periodically to stay in tune with a runners' changing goals. For example, the system can tailor the advice given, based on improvement and shifting goals. As an example, the tracker can adjust itself and give advice accordingly, if the runner misses a training or when the weather is too cold to go for a run.

Conclusion

In this paper, the dimensions of data experience of amateur runners in relation to their data requirements were explored. Even though there are studies that explore how people experience fitness trackers, the novelty of this study was the exploration of the importance of "data experience" for amateur runners and perhaps more interesting the relations between the type of data the amateur runners expect to see and the qualities of data.

With this research agenda, it was hoped to explore how to better design systems to offer engaging experience and to improve runners' training. It was found that usefulness, interactivity, personalization, connectivity and accuracy of data are the main dimensions of data experience of amateur runners. Future trackers could go beyond the simple display of information to include personalized prompts for individual runners or case-specific solutions. They could represent a person's ideal self in terms of who

they want to be, satisfy them emotionally, and prevent them from becoming injured during running. They could offer data features that people can customize to their personal needs. By understanding the specific runner, the tracker needs to adapt itself to runners' expectations. In this way, a tracker can analyze personal data and make suggestions accordingly.

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The Gentleman. A prosocial assistance system to promote considerate driving

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Abstract Supportive and considerate driving is the bedrock of road safety. Unfortunately, considerate driving is not always easy to accomplish in the rush of everyday traffic. Surprisingly, while there are rules, regulations and campaigns to promote considerate driving, the car itself often plays only a minor role. Here safety is considered foremost a matter of caring about the driver and passengers in the car rather than about the more vulnerable cyclists or pedestrians outside the car. To question this, we developed the general idea of *prosocial assistance systems*. These systems create opportunities for drivers to experience prosocial behavior as enjoyable and meaningful. In the present paper, we discuss *The Gentleman*. It supports the driver in giving way to pedestrians even under adverse conditions. We report how we identified giving way as a relevant prosocial practice and present an ideal experience design based on a series of empirical explorations.

Keywords *Experience design, Automotive, Prosocial behavior, Considerate driving, Behavior change*

Introduction

Paragraph 1 of the German Road Traffic Regulations (StVO) emphasizes that participation in road traffic requires constant cautiousness and courtesy. In addition, every road user is obliged to neither injure, endanger nor impede other traffic members beyond what seems unavoidable. In short: The “ideal” road user is attentive, considerate and supportive towards others, especially the more vulnerable. Of course, reality is different. While traffic becomes more dense at least in Germany (Kraftfahrt-Bundesamt, 2013), hindrances, misunderstandings, and breaches of rules increase, leading to stress, conflict, anger and aggressive driving (Benmimoun, Neunzig, & Maag, 2004; Deffenbacher, Lynch, Filetti, Dahlen, & Oetting, 2003; Galovski, Malta, & Blanchard, 2006; Parkinson, 2001; Shinar, 2007; Shinar & Compton, 2004).

Since attentive, considerate and supportive driving is crucial to road safety, exploring new ways of promoting considerate driving seems important. From a psychological perspective, considerate driving is a form of prosocial behavior. Prosocial behavior circumscribes a “broad range of actions intended to benefit one or more people other than oneself for example behaviors such as helping, comforting, sharing, cooperation, philanthropy” (Batson & Powell, 2003, p. 463). Prosocial driving is defined as “driving behaviors that potentially protect the wellbeing of passengers, other drivers, and pedestrians, and that promote effective cooperation with others in the

driving environment” (Harris et al., 2014, p. 4). In contrast to aggressive driving, only few studies exist in transportation, which focus on prosocial behavior in the broadest sense (e.g., Benmimoun et al., 2004; Ellinghaus, 1986; Ross & Antonowicz, 2004). To promote prosocial behavior in traffic, it seems necessary to make drivers (and others) aware of their own actions and to support the implementation of “better” behaviors (Ellinghaus, 1986, p. 121). In this sense, prosocial driving is an example of designing for change (Hassenzahl & Laschke, 2015; Tromp, Hekkert, & Verbeek, 2011).

Road users are highly affected by the built environment (e.g., Roessger, Schade, Schlag, & Gehlert, 2011, p. 111). As a consequence, structural changes (e.g., roundabouts, shared spaces) are the major tactic to instill considerate driving. However, the car as a platform for interventions is promising, too. It offers a wide range of opportunities to provide feedback to the driver and to suggest alternative, more prosocial courses of action. Quite contrary to this, contemporary car design focuses on the driver and the passengers, their space and safety, and follows an aggressive, individualistic ideal (Redshaw, 2011).

To counteract this, we propose the notion of *prosocial assistance systems*. Similarly to well-known assistance systems designed for the driver's safety and comfort, we suggest to explore assistance aimed at helping the driver to act more considerate, fair and supportive. A

Figure 1. Initial exploration.

first example of this is the *Alliance of the Last Gentlemen* (Knobel et al., 2013). It encourages prosocial driving by suggesting potential ways of behaving (e.g., giving way), activating related norms (e.g., become a role model, one of the last gentlemen on the road) and providing positive feedback, if acts of considerate driving are performed. Another example is *HörMal* (Eckoldt et al., 2015), a system to increase the driver's attention and to activate relevant norms by augmenting the often overlooked German traffic sign "Attention: Children" (i.e., school zones) with the sound of playing children rendered through the car's audio system.

In the present paper, we explore the idea of prosocial assistance further through *The Gentleman*. This is a conceptual design, which assists drivers in giving way to pedestrians under adverse conditions. We describe our inspiration, report the empirical exploration of a minimal prototype, and present an ideal interaction. Note that the name *Gentleman* is not a thoughtless reference to gendered stereotypes about helping behavior. Aggressive driving is a rather male phenomenon (Shinar & Compton, 2004). In this respect, the *Gentleman's* intention is to playfully appeal to the self-image of particular male drivers. In addition, there is a strong asymmetry in the vulnerability of people inside and outside cars, which creates a striking imbalance of power. The *Gentleman* connotes a particular idea of prosocial behavior, namely the gentleman-like forgoing of a right from a position of strength. This also applies to women drivers, since it is more about an imbalance of power among drivers and pedestrians than about an imbalance of power among women and men.

Being a gentleman driver by giving way to pedestrians

Identifying prosocial practices in traffic

While the notion of prosocial assistance implies that people need support in behaving considerately in traffic, prosocial behavior should not be enforced, but rather framed as an opportunity to experience an enjoyable and meaningful moment in everyday life (Hassenzahl, 2010; Hassenzahl et al., 2013).

A first step was to collect individual experiences of prosocial practices in traffic. In an online study, we asked 109 participants (72% female, age: M=30, min=18, max=59) to describe positive or negative prosocial moments in traffic – either from the perspective of a "giver" or "receiver". We collected forty-five positive experiences and used them as inspiration. One experience mentioned repeatedly by both, driver (giver) and pedestrian (receiver), was to allow pedestrians to safely cross the road by slowing down or stopping.

Understanding the practice of giving way to pedestrians

Based on the collected anecdotes, we distilled an essence of this positive and meaningful moment and transformed it into an "experience pattern" (Hassenzahl et al., 2013) – a blueprint of an "ideal" way of letting pedestrians cross the road. To support this, we conducted a first exploration (see Figure 1). We accompanied three participants in their cars (two women age of 34 [X1] and 30 [X2] years and a man age of 31 [X3], all participants held a driving license for at least 12 years). Without detailed information about the focus of the exploration, the participants were instructed to drive several times along a shopping

street during business hours. Here, crossing pedestrians are common. Besides observing the driver's and pedestrians' actions, we carried out a semi-structured, narrative interview with the drivers during and after the trip. The aim was to get a detailed impression of the interaction between driver and pedestrian (e.g., gestures, timing) as well as a notion of what distinguishes enjoyable and meaningful instances of letting a pedestrian cross from the less satisfactory.

Altogether, we observed 14 spontaneous instances of letting pedestrians cross the road. These revealed certain key elements. First, of course, the driver needs to notice the pedestrian's intention to cross the road. The starting point of their "dialogue" is the moment the pedestrian turns towards the lane and notices the approaching car. If the driver is willing to yield to the pedestrian, she reduces speed until the car comes to a stop in front of the pedestrian. Ideally, the speed reduction is done in a way that can be clearly interpreted. If so, the pedestrian understands it as a permission to cross the road. In many cases, the pedestrian then seeks eye contact and the driver clarifies his intention through a hand gesture. Typically, the driver points her hand at the pedestrian and subsequently performs a movement to the other side of the road. The pedestrian responds by raising a hand or giving a nod before crossing the road. This is not only a gesture of affirmation but also gratitude, which seems especially important in this situation. As one driver remarked: *"I really like the situation when the pedestrian recognizes my intention and honors it with a gesture. Because in some way, I want to receive gratitude for it"* (X1). The driver continues her journey, when the pedestrian has cleared the area in front of her vehicle.

In sum, letting a pedestrian pass is a social exchange (Smith, Mackie, & Claypool, 2014) between the driver and the pedestrian. The driver offers a benefit to the pedestrian, who in turn provides a positive feedback (i.e., a "thank you") as an affective reward to satisfy implicit notions of reciprocity. For the driver, a satisfying transaction reinforces the considerate practice (Knobel et al., 2013). To run smoothly, this requires being able to communicate nonverbally. While communication at daytime is at least in principle possible, twilight or darkness creates numerous difficulties. Blinding headlights hamper the pedestrians' ability to make eye contact and to recognize the gestures of drivers in the dark interiors of their cars. Other typical communication "tools" already available, such as headlight flashing and horn signals are ambiguous or have negative connotations. For example, flashing the headlights as prompt to cross the road can be perceived as impatience of the driver leading to the impression of being rushed. In addition, pedestrians perceive the expressive design of many cars combined with bright headlights as aggressive (Bayley, Curtis, Lupton, & Wright, 2005). While a smiling driver politely gestures to prompt the pedestrian to cross the road, her car tells the opposite story through its design. All this leads to miscommunication and ambiguity. In addition, even after having safely crossed the street, the lack of eye

contact and direct communication creates difficulties in expressing gratitude. All in all, this may lead to a quite unsatisfactory experience, despite best intentions.

A minimal prototype to improve giving way under adverse conditions

We created a minimal prototype to further explore the general idea of the *Gentleman*. It had two features. In the dark, the car's appearance is largely determined by its headlights. Thus, when the driver decided to give way to a participant and was already slowing down, we automatically switched to parking lights. This was to clearly communicate the driver's intention to the pedestrian and to create a feeling of safety by letting the car appear more passive. It also initiated the dialogue between both. In addition, the driver was illuminated by an additional interior light located in the sun visor above the driver's head. This is an important precondition for disambiguating the situation through hand gestures and eye contact as well as for facilitating the social exchange. We carried out an exploration of our minimal prototype. An examiner sitting in the back seat of the car simulated the functionality of the "system". The headlights were dimmed the moment the driver started to slow down and the additional lighting was activated when the driver made a gesture towards the pedestrian.

Four people explored the prototype (two women aged 44 [P1] and 43 [P2]; two men aged 30 [P3] and 34 [P4]). All participants held their driving license for at least 12 years and possessed their own car. The set-up can be best described as role play in the field with uninitiated lay participants. In each case the role play was performed with two of the participants and took place after sunset (the earliest was at 9:30pm in the month of July, 2013). Each participant played both, the role of the driver and the pedestrian. The role was determined randomly at the beginning of every new trial.

We specified a circular route through the city to guarantee multiple encounters between "driver" and "pedestrian". The pedestrian was asked to cross the road at the same spot each time (see Figure 2). This gave both, the pedestrian and the driver, the opportunity to get used to the prototype and the situation created through it. After at least six encounters the driver and the pedestrian switched roles. The entire trip was recorded on video from various angles both inside and outside the car. During and after the exploration, we conducted half-structured, narrative interviews, focusing on individual experience and meaning.

What was noticed first was the unusual response of the headlights. One participant in the role of the "driver" said: *"At the beginning, I found it very confusing that the headlights were turned off. And then I couldn't see the pedestrian anymore"* (P1). Another said: *"Suddenly the lights went out. Well, now he can see me, but I see just nothing. But I'm still on the road. I still want to be able to see and to know that everything is all right in front of the car"* (P4).

Figure 2. An empirical exploration of a minimal prototype.

Obviously, drivers were confused when the headlights automatically switched to low beam without warning. They found the resulting poorer light condition disconcerting. Now pedestrians and the area in front of the car were significantly less visible. For the driver, it was as if the headlights had been switched off. This gave rise to an unsettling sense of not being in control of the situation.

For the pedestrians, on the other hand, dimming the headlights was a clear signal. One remarked: “[...] the light goes out, the car goes into a passive state [...] It appears as if the engine stops. Almost. And if the engine has stopped, one can safely cross the street. This makes it clearer” (P4). Another said: “[...] because dimming the lights implies, that the car parks. Or at least implies the intention not to drive for a while” (P2). The parking lights let the car appear more passive, less aggressive, and therefore less dangerous. “This provides a moment of calmness. It gives me time. [...] A signal to smoothly cross the street. This settles the situation” (P2). The passivity created room for a dialogue and reduced the pressure on the pedestrian to cross the street quickly. A “driver” said: “This allows for communication with the pedestrian. It is courteous. I am in fact provided with the right of way” (P4). Through this, the driver was perceived as considerate and courteous.

Over the course of the exploration, the drivers became aware of the value of this gesture for the pedestrian. This even helped them to accept the disadvantage of the poorer light conditions: “I find it somewhat too dark, [...] but now I can signal that he can go. He sees that I get slower. This appears as if I would park. And now he knows, that he can go” (P3). Another

participant said: “It is uncommon because normally the headlights stay on. But after the second or third time it became normal” (P1).

Other than switching the headlights to low beam, which happened “automatically”, the interior communication light was activated when the driver made a hand gesture of “giving way”. Spontaneously, however, this gesture was made only by two participants. The other participants either flashed their headlights to signal to the pedestrian or made no gesture at all and simply waited for the pedestrian to cross the street. During the exploration, participants were then explicitly instructed to use the hand gesture. One “driver” explained: “I saw him standing there, slowed down. I waited to see whether he would go [...] when he didn’t go ... simply made an additional hand gesture and that [...] apparently [...] activated the light and he seemed to see the hand gesture. Or saw it more clearly. [He] was ascertained and crossed the street” (P4).

During the last three rounds, all participants experienced the effectiveness of the “interior communication light”. The pedestrians responded to the drivers’ hand gestures by nodding briefly or waving an arm in thanks. From the driver’s perspective, all participants noted that the “interior communication light” improved communication with the pedestrians and made it more explicit. It made drivers feel confident about being able to signal clearly to the pedestrians that they can cross the street safely. This was also experienced by the pedestrians. One pedestrian said: “It provides a feeling of safety, because you can see the driver” (P3). Or: “It is a courteous gesture somehow. Because it clearly says: ‘Ok, you can cross here now’” (P4). All this clearly disambiguated the situation: “Yes all is clearer. It is more obvious [for the pedestrian] [the concept] enables a better communication” (P1). Or: “I found the situation comforting. You do not need to do more, the pedestrian is aware that I stop. And knows, that I recognize him and give him all the time he needs to cross the street” (P2). “Lighting up the interior, for me is a kind of polite gesture. Because it is a way to reveal yourself. To step out of your anonymity. It is like making a step towards the pedestrian” (P4).

Note that one participant (P2) also expressed concerns about becoming exposed: “I ask myself, do I want the car to act like this? That people can see that I am alone in my car. That I am traveling on my own. [...] The darkness in the interior gives me a sense of security” (P2).

From a driver’s perspective *The Gentleman* definitely improved the interaction with the pedestrian. It provided clear signals about intentions and facilitated more direct communication through eye contact and gestures. However, switching to parking lights was not the solution. It appeared to the drivers as if switching the headlights off entirely. From a pedestrian’s perspective, the encounter with the car appeared less dangerous through the concept. The dimming of the headlights was perceived as a sign of passivity. Pedestrians can cross the street safe and unhurried.

Figure 3. Storyboard of the ideal interaction .

This sense of safety was further enhanced by the interior light, which enabled the pedestrian to better interpret the driver's intention, allowed for more communication, and reduced anonymity – all viewed as quite a courteous. In sum, all participants (in both roles, driver and pedestrian) experienced the concept positively. It disambiguated and relaxed the situation and provided a courteous feeling and a sense of safety.

The Gentleman – an ideal interaction

Our exploration became the basis for the design of a more refined, ideal interaction. The key challenge was to create a lighting, which lets the car appear more passive and inviting from the pedestrian's perspective,

but at the same time creates good visibility from the driver's perspective.

Figure 3 summarizes *The Gentleman* in a storyboard. The driver recognizes a pedestrian and intends to give way (Scene A). While slowing down, the headlights are lowered to create a deferential impression and to mitigate the danger and aggressiveness of contemporary exterior car design (B). This will also signal the driver's intention to stop for the pedestrian by dipping the headlights already with the beginning of braking. Upon stopping, the dipped headlights become indirect lights to illuminate the surrounding and the road in front of the car, creating the

Figure 4. The F015 Concept Car from Mercedes Benz, Las Vegas, January 2015.

impression of a path for the pedestrian. This inviting path, however, stops at the left, since the driver cannot take the responsibility for parts of the road not in front of the own car. The moment the car comes to a full stop, a special interior light illuminates the driver's face (C). An indirect light illuminates the pedestrians' face without blinding her. This facilitates eye contact and communication through gestures. As already said before, this is not only important for disambiguating the situation, but also for clearly expressing gratitude, which seems crucial for the driver to experience the social exchange as satisfactory (D). The pedestrian crosses the street, paying attention to the oncoming traffic or other cars attempting to overtake the vehicle (E). As soon as the driver continues the journey, headlights revert to normal and the interior light is switched-off (F).

Summary and conclusion

The Gentleman is an example of what we call a *prosocial assistance system*. Their general idea is to support drivers in being more considerate, attentive and courteous towards other traffic members. To this end, we identified giving way to pedestrians as one already existing and potentially suitable practice. *The Gentleman's* aim is to improve the direct communication between driver and pedestrian even under adverse conditions (i.e., in twilight, darkness). An initial exploratory study, which simulated key aspects of the concept, showed that *The Gentleman* is able to improve the communication between drivers and pedestrians with minimum means. Pedestrians as well as drivers perceived the situation created through *The Gentlemen* as meaningful. From the pedestrian's point of view the car becomes more passive and less dangerous. The visual contact enables the pedestrian to more clearly understand the driver's intention. Consequently, the concept creates a feeling of safety,

which is attributed to the driver/car and perceived as courteous. From the driver's point of view, participants understood *The Gentleman* as a designed opportunity to behave courteously. It assists by clarifying intentions and the situation, as well as creating more face-to-face-like contact with the pedestrian, thereby intensifying the encounter. A next step would be to transfer the ideal interaction design into a tangible prototype and develop it through further studies.

The Gentleman as well as the explorations described in this paper were carried out in summer 2013 in cooperation with BMW research. Interestingly, in January 2015 Mercedes Benz presented the F015 concept car, which – among other features – started to address the topic of clearly giving way to pedestrians by projecting a crosswalk onto the road (see Figure 4). While we are not entirely convinced by projecting an actual crosswalk onto the street, since the driver or the car can never take responsibility for a second lane and, thus, the crosswalk metaphor will never fully hold, it is promising that the topic gains some broader recognition by car manufacturers. Note, however, that the F015 is an autonomous car, and this interaction is not meant as a way to promote prosocial driving and satisfying social exchange on the road, but as a polite gesture of a robotic car. Maybe tellingly, there seems to be higher need to let an autonomous car appear considerate than to provide drivers with tools to become more considerate.

Prosocial assistance systems embody an attentive, considerate, yet helping behavior. They assist the driver in the actual implementation (i.e. the action). Their aim is to relax road traffic and to increase road safety. Prosocial behavior is framed as a potential source of positive and meaningful experiences rather than as an annoying necessity. Current headlight

prototypes and the in-series production of high power headlights show that the realization of *The Gentleman* does not require any additional development of technology. New headlight developments are already called “light-based driver assistance systems” (Amsel, Florissen, & Pietzonka, 2010), which actively assist the driver to avoid dangerous situations. They are able to recognize oncoming cars and cut them out of their cone of light. The basic idea of *prosocial assistance systems* is thus not a technical, but a social innovation. It doesn’t require new vehicle technologies, but rethinking and reframing the “emotional” use of cars. In this sense, the challenge is not to implement *The Gentleman*, but to convince premium car manufacturers to abandon the culture of “aggressive individualism”. This culture is largely based on the implicit assumption that the typical customer would not get excited about “prosocial” driving. However, we do not share this pessimistic view. In our opinion, it is crucial for the automotive industry to face the requirements of social sustainability in addition to the already administered requirements of environmental sustainability. And it is certainly possible for interaction design and experience design to make helping others enjoyable.

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Designing for motivation and wellbeing: Reversal theory, doors, and colors

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Abstract Reversal theory recognizes the dynamic nature of the emotional experience of objects and spaces, and establishes a framework for design that can be used to enhance wellbeing. It also directly acknowledges the important effect that personal and social context has on motivations, affect and mental health. Reversal theory's focus on links between motivation and ensuing emotional states and behaviors, provides an important theoretical structure for the study of the individual's experience over time. The major tenets of reversal theory are discussed and their applicability by design practitioners reviewed. Ways that reversal theory can inform the design of architectural elements, for example, doors, and the development of interior design features, for example, via surface color selection, are discussed.

Keywords *Reversal theory, Wellbeing, Architecture, Interior design, Color*

Introduction

As many people in the developed and developing world become more concerned about using diminishing resources more effectively and efficiently, design that initiates and supports different motivational states, as appropriate or as needed, becomes more important.

One way in which different experiences can be organized and understood is in terms of the contrasting things that people want to experience at different times and in different situations, and such psychological desires will be what is meant here by 'motivational state.' The term comes from reversal theory (Apter, 1982, 2001, 2007), which is a general theory of motivation, emotion, and personality. This will provide the guiding structure for the present paper, which will apply it to architecture and interior design. Motivational states go beyond motivations as such in that they are associated with different ways of seeing the world and different styles of action. We should also notice that they are different from moods, the term 'mood' usually being used to refer to pessimism or optimism, thus being orthogonal to motivational states, which may be associated with any level of hope or despair.

The basic idea is that different architectural and interior design features will play a part in inducing different motivational states, and may also play a part in satisfying them emotionally. They are not the only stimuli to do so, but they are usually important. For example, a church induces a serious state of mind during a wedding and the need to do something significant, and also provides a setting that makes this emotional significance possible. Sometimes we choose the design situations in which we find ourselves for a reason tied to a motivational state. At other times these states just occur, outside our normal control.

Using the concept of motivational states to inform design decisions is consistent with the growing worldwide interest in positive design—the development of spaces, objects, and experiences that increase user subjective well-being and the likelihood of human flourishing. As Desmet and Pohlmeier say: "The intention [of positive design] is not to design so that people always feel good and never feel bad. Instead, it is to design such that people have a chance to embrace all the dimensions of life, including hardship, adversity, and opportunity" (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013, p. 16). The desirability of experiencing a full variety of different emotions, rather than just a few pleasant ones, is also a central idea in reversal theory.

Environmental psychologists have started on the road to linking design elements and emotional response to them. Their solutions to date have come up short because they view humans too simplistically and do not acknowledge the full richness of possible emotional experience and "the changeability of human nature" (Apter, 2007 p. xii). Reversal theory comprehensively reflects human beings' dynamic affective experiences, as described in the sections that follow.

The way that people change in their motivational states often arises from moving from one behavioral setting to another, for example from the office to the restaurant, the playground to the classroom. A complication is that a space can be used at different times and by different people as the context for varying activities. The same function room at a hotel can be used for the professional meeting or family birthday party. Design that directly acknowledges these variations in use and brings to bear features that will support these different states at different times increases the likelihood that object and space users will have affirming emotional experiences.

In our technologically advanced world, doors are an important architectural element in our experience. Which motivational state prevails will often depend among other things on various features of the settings - size of rooms, type of flooring, etc., all of whose psychological implications are cognitively integrated to holistically influence human experience and wellbeing. The door is the first contact with the new space and is therefore especially important in inducing a new state. Although many architectural features affect motivations, e.g. windows, pillars, carpets, here we are concentrating on doors, which will be used as illustrative of general concepts. We will also review links between surface colors seen and human experiences. In this way we shall be able to show how reversal theory can elucidate the effects of design both in terms of motivational states and of emotions. We are therefore not dealing here with a full range of architectural features (as in Koolhaas, 2014), or all forms of sensory stimulation, but have taken an example of each to illustrate the approach. But first we need to introduce reversal theory.

The reversal theory approach

Reversal theory is a useful system to inform the development of spaces where people will have their desired experiences (Fokkinga and Desmet, 2014a, b). Reversal theory posits that we move between different motivations for our actions in our daily lives, and in pursuing these contrasting needs we see the world in different ways. This means that, in a sense, each of us is a different person at different moments, and that over time we display diverse and even contradictory personalities: "We differ not only from each other, but also from ourselves. . . . [Reversal theory] offers a systematic description of the various ways that we can experience the world and act in it. The key idea is that there is a universal set of distinctive modes of interaction with the world, each one anchored in a different fundamental motivation. In the normal way of things and in our own unique fashion, we all move around between these different 'ways of being'" (Apter, 2007, pp. xi-xii). Reversal theory recognizes that every space/object use does not take place in the same psychological context.

Reversal theory recognizes four sets of experiences, each of which is identified by two opposite motivational states (Apter, 2001, 2007). At a particular point in time, one of each pair of states will be active, although some of the active states are having a more significant influence on overall psychological state than others. They have become the focus of attention. A person can move backwards and forwards between motivational states as an experience develops, and also from a focus on one pair of motivational states to another. This will all become clearer when we look at specific motivational states.

The eight motivational states

Reversal theory posits four pairs of opposite motivational states – states in which people want opposite things and see the world in reverse ways as a consequence (Apter, 1982). Note that these states are subjective and that reversal theory is therefore phenomenological in approach.

The first pair of states are the telic and paratelic motivational states. These can be conceptualized as involving diametrically opposed sources of pleasure in action. When someone is in a telic state, they derive satisfaction from the perception that they are advancing toward the completion of a goal and the actual, ultimate attainment of the acknowledged objective. Progress and improvement are important to someone in a telic state. If a person is in a paratelic state, pleasure is, instead, primarily derived from the activity in process, rather than from progress toward that goal - for example dancing or wine tasting. This means that sensory and kinesthetic experiences are important in the paratelic state, as is the feeling of being 'alive' in the moment. The telic state can be described by the adjective "serious," while the most appropriate adjective to describe the paratelic state is "playful." (Apter, 1982, 2007).

Emotionally, it is preferable to experience the telic state under low arousal conditions, which are experienced as relaxing; in highly energized states, the telic state gives rise to anxiety. The reverse is true for the optimal experience of the paratelic state; in a stimulating environment, the paratelic state is associated with excitement, while in a more relaxing environment boredom can ensue from the paratelic state. Research has shown that people prefer sensory experiences consistent with their motivational state, more relaxing experiences while they're in telic ones and more energizing conditions when they're in a paratelic state (e.g. Walters, Apter, and Svebak, 1982).

In all cases, the state is a precondition for an emotion. As Apter (2014) details, in the reversal theory system, after the telic state is induced, if there is high arousal, anxiety is experienced. It is not the case that after a person begins to feel anxious they enter the telic state, since it is the telic state which is a prerequisite for anxiety.

Reversal theory's second pair of states are the conforming and negativistic ones (Apter, 1981, 2001). This meta-motivational state moves beyond one's physical state to thoughts about one's own behavior. Actual behaviors are compared to relevant expectations or rules imposed by the salient culture. These rules may be any kind of subjective expectation, norm, social pressure, regulation, constraint, or requirement as seen by the person concerned. In a negativistic state people enjoy behaving in ways that violate such social conventions and experience their actions as a kind of freedom and independence. Conversely, in the conformist state a person likes acting in ways that seem to align with societal norms, and it would be unpleasant not to do so. As with all motivational states, the negativistic state defines what one wants, rather than what one actually experiences. This is why it is called a motivational state. The negativistic state is essentially rebellious and the conforming state compliant.

The next pair of states relate to "felt transaction outcome," which means the degree to which one perceives oneself to be gaining or losing in some ongoing transaction. The autic state is self-centered

while the other-centered state is called “alloic.” In the alloic state, one’s primary concern is that someone else should benefit from what is going on. If one is in the autic state the concern is for the self; gain will be felt as pride at having done well and loss as humiliation. In the alloic state any gain at the expense of others leads to the emotional state of shame while loss at the hands of others is experienced as pleasant modesty. It is important to realize that the other with whom we are interacting can be a person, a group of people, a situation, or an object. When dealing with an object, a person is most likely to be in the autic state, since it is difficult to identify with a screen and keyboard, for example. All the same, possessions can be treated in a caring selfless sort of way; in other words, they can be loved and attention devoted to them. This makes it possible to interact with an object in the alloic state (Apter, 2014).

Finally, there are two different ways of experiencing relationships. One is oriented to feelings of strength and power and called the “mastery” state. Being in it does not mean that you are powerful, but that this is what you want at a particular moment. The other state has to do with whether you have close emotional relationships; it is called the “sympathy” state. Being in the sympathy state implies that sympathy is what you want at that moment, not that you are necessarily experiencing it. In the mastery state, then, the goal is to feel powerful, and transactions are evaluated accordingly. In the sympathy state the overriding aim is to feel that others have fond feelings for you, or you for them, and transactions are, again, assessed in light of this desire. People in the mastery state may be described as “competitive,” while those in the sympathy state can be seen as “affectionate.”

“Reversals” are switches from one motivational state to its opposite within a pair, and these “flips” can occur fairly frequently. As mentioned earlier, they can result as one moves between different behavioral settings, say from bed to the breakfast room. More generally reversals occur when events happen that call on different states of mind, for example when someone tells a joke, or offers you a cigarette, or is rude. As Kerr, Hayashi, Matsumoto, and Miyamoto, report, reversal theory “is important for understanding human psychological responses to different types of locations, settings and activities” (Kerr, Hayashi, Matsumoto, & Miyamoto, 2002, p. 361). They state that their findings indicate that different motivational “states and arousal levels are affected by different settings” (p. 361).

Reversals can also occur spontaneously, with no obvious environmental cause, although one must suppose that internal processes of change are taking place. For example, one might be looking after a sick friend and at a certain moment, with nothing in the environment changing, suddenly want to pay more attention to one’s own needs. The alloic (other-oriented) state has, as it were, satiated and the autic (self-oriented) state has taken over. As a result one’s immediate emotions might switch from feelings of virtue to feelings of resentment at one’s friend.

So at any one time, there will be four active motivational states, one from each pair. For example a child doing a classroom test might experience telic, conforming, mastery and autic states at the same time, although one of them will be typically the dominating state, e.g., the telic state. However, the focus may change as the environmental demands change, for instance the teacher demands that the children copy something from the blackboard, which might induce a focal change to the conforming state in the children, all the other states remaining unchanged. Or perhaps the teacher makes a joke. This time the change from the telic to the paratelic state would be a reversal (from telic to paratelic) rather than a focal change. All this may seem complicated, but this complexity is missed by approaches that do not take into account the changeability of the way that motivation is experienced.

Doors

Doors serve multiple purposes in our physical and social environments. They not only allow the flow of light, air, information, and people into and out of a space, but send nonverbal, silent messages via their form and design. Doors are found inside structures and at the barriers between inside and outside. In this text, we shall focus on exterior ones because they have more generally been the focus of social science research (for example, Marsden, 1999).

Doors, whether domestic, commercial, or civic, are an example of an architectural design element that can take different forms and induce and support various motivational states. They are particularly of interest to reversal theory, because doors are often the site of reversals as one moves from one environment to another.

Their form and position have more complex implications than one might at first suppose. Doors are open or closed, which is another way of saying exposing or concealing, or allowing passage or not allowing passage. They may have an owner inside and a visitor outside, an owner both inside and outside at different times, a visitor both inside and outside at different times, and, less usually, an owner outside and visitor inside. The owner usually owns the door as well as the area behind the door.

The state invoked by the door should be the same as the state invoked by the building as a whole, otherwise the architecture will be psychologically incoherent and most probably negatively evaluated; the mental implications of all physical stimuli in a space are integrated cognitively so that they can, ideally, in a coordinated way, influence mental state (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1982). The door acts as a frame to the building and therefore should not contradict it. This frame-like quality is emphasized where there is an arch around the door.

Environmental factors are powerful nonverbal communicators, as evidenced by the work of Moezzi and Goins (2011). Doors can induce and subsequently support a message and state after they are viewed and, generally subsequently, experienced haptically or

in some other manner. If the people who own and visit a door, for example, those who are on opposite sides of it, share cultural context, they will “hear” the same nonverbal messages when they see, touch, etc., a door. For example, all will consistently perceive when a door indicates mastery; the visitor will see the owner as motivated by mastery and the owner will see himself/herself as motivated by mastery. A stout door with bars might help the owner to feel powerful (mastery), but it might produce feelings in the visitor that are more like mastery losing, or perhaps the visitor’s emotional state becomes that of conforming.

The focus in this text is on the state that doors invoke in visitors to a space, not in the owners of it. In some cases, for example when arriving at a health clinic, the visitor will already be in a given motivational state, with certain needs, and how the door can help satisfy these needs is a significant part of our discussion.

Also, just as the individual does not have enduring motivational states, we may suppose that a door has different effects on different people at different times, or even on the same person at different times. The person viewing the door could interpret information they’re drawing from it in different ways because of their personal context. For example, seeing the same healthcare door before and after a diagnosis of cancer is likely to be linked with a different motivational state. Or, perhaps in the face of a stout door, an individual in the autic state might feel that they are losing, but if they are in the alloic state, and empathize with the strength of the owner, they could feel good.

Doors and states

Let us suppose we have a closed door and a visitor coming to the door. What features of the door are likely to induce each motivational state in that visitor? This is the situation of most interest to the designer. We shall suggest here some features that might induce and even support each state; although personal and social factors also, for example, help establish state (Apter, 1982). This will provide structure for future research; state-inducing features discussed are derived from the environmental psychology literature. It should be noted that door examples provided are not the only doors that might induce or support a motivational state and that doors are not the only influence on state.

Telic state

The aim of the telic door is to get the visitor into a serious state of mind. The building might be a law court, or a hospital, or a bank. A door that induces a telic state might be larger than normal (consistent with the research of Lakoff & Johnson, 1999) or be made from expensive materials. The door on the entrance to the main headquarters of the Bank of England meets these criteria. Double rather than single doors, as on churches, are likely to be used to help induce the telic state.

Paratelic state

The aim of a paratelic state-inducing door is to get the visitor into the playful state of mind. It might be found

at a cinema, a casino, a sports stadium, or a swimming pool. These sorts of doors could feature bolder, more saturated colors (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994) and curved shapes (Dazkir & Read, 2012). They could be unusually designed, for example wide doors or doors that don’t swing on a hinge but roll along overhead pipes to open and close (i.e., barn doors). Their hardware is likely to be more whimsical than telic state-inducing doors. These sorts of doors are likely to seem less practical, and are more likely to be installed purely for aesthetic enjoyment by the user group. Doors to many attractions at Disneyland fit this criterion.

Conforming state

The aim of conforming state-inducing doors is to get the visitor into a compliant state of mind. They are probable at a secure building at an airport, or a police station, or a church. These doors are likely to be symmetrical (Bajaj & Bond, 2016), large, and elevated (Lakoff & Johnson, 1999). They might also be revolving since these entrances are more effortful to use; entry needs to be carefully timed. A door without a knob, that is opened using something like a retinal scan, and only openable in the case of that appropriate retinal scan, would also be likely to induce a conforming state.

Negativistic state

The aim of a negativistic state-inducing door is to get the visitor into a rebellious state of mind. It might be used on a bar or club. This sort of door might be graffiti covered (intentionally by owners, not by vandals) and more rectilinear than curvilinear (Dazkir & Read, 2012). Its form is likely to bring to the owner’s individuality to mind because of the way it is personalized. An example: A metallic, spiky holiday wreath, without natural or curving elements on a door might induce the negativistic state. No information might be provided to visitors about hours of operation on a negativistic state-inducing door, for example. This door might be so narrow it is hard to pass into or out of a space. It should be painted in saturated not bright colors (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994).

Autic state

The aim of the autic state-inducing door is to get the visitor to give priority to his/her own needs. This sort of door is appropriate at a spa, a hairdresser, or an emergency ward. It would feature a prominent welcome sign and, as relevant, directions for users, such as operating hours. These doors would be familiar in materials and scale, for example, painted wood for front doors for residences. Studies have repeatedly linked familiarity and comfort (Devlin, 2010). The form and style of these doors would vary over time based on current societal needs/practices. Another example is a bead curtain door, easily passable by all, as well as any door that can’t be locked or blocked – but of course these free-entry options aren’t really practical for the outer door of most buildings.

Alloic state

The aim of the alloic state-inducing door is to get the visitor to give priority to others. The building might be

a hospital waiting room or a charity shop. In this case, a “thank you” sign might greet visitors, or a sign saying “Please give patients priority through these doors.” Frosted glass may also help the visitor to be aware of the position of others on the other side of the door, thus not pushing the door into them.

Sympathy state

The aim of the sympathy state-inducing door is to get the visitor into an agreeable state of mind. It might be used on a hospital or a kindergarten. It should feature not very saturated but relatively bright colors (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994) and be easy to open. Doors that open automatically are seen as very welcoming (Ju & Takayama, 2009). Just as rectilinear elements/decorations on challenging doors would establish a feeling of hostility, curvy ones here would be linked to more comforting and comfortable experiences (Dazkir & Read, 2012). Doors with visible wood grain would be sympathy inducing (Fell, 2010).

Mastery state

The aim with a mastery-state inducing door is to get the visitor into the competitive controlling state of mind. It might be used at a sporting venue, such as a swimming pool or golf course, or at a boardroom. Doors likely to induce mastery can be reminiscent of the doors to old time castles - massive and impenetrable, with the materials ranging from heavy/relatively coarse timbers to metal to something else that seems cold and hard. The doors could seem very mechanical and functional, perhaps gliding open as the visitor approached. They could also contain a peephole, as in Prohibition speakeasies, which might intimidate the visitor.

We should bear in mind that the relationship between doors (or any architectural feature) and motivational state, can become complicated. For one thing, there will normally be different cues in a given situation and the feature of interest, say a door, must compete with these others (windows, ceiling, etc.) in bringing about or inhibiting a reversal on one or another reversal dimension. Secondly, the same feature may support different states, for example a fireplace may support both the paratelic and mastery states, and this relationship may even change from one time to another in a given person. And of course the relationships may vary significantly from one person to another.

Colors and states

Surface colors have a significant effect on mental state (Valdez and Mehrabian, 1994). As a result, this interior design element is an important consideration for people applying reversal theory (Apter, 2014).

Valdez and Mehrabian (1994) empirically established a universal link between color saturation and brightness and pleasantness and energy level. Colors that are not very saturated but relatively bright have been linked to relaxation (and therefore support desirable telic state experiences) while seeing colors that are saturated but not very bright are pleasantly energizing to look at (and therefore support desirable paratelic state experiences). Colors that are less saturated seem

to have more gray in them than colors that are more saturated. For example, khaki green is less saturated than Kelly green. Responses to several hues also seem to be universal (Aslam, 2006; Elliot et al., 2007; Lichtenfeld et al., 2012). Hues are collections of wavelengths gathered into sets and named, such as green and orange.

Telic state

As used in many domestic and commercial applications, grays are the sort of not very saturated but bright color that Valdez and Mehrabian have empirically tied to calmer, relaxed emotional states (1994). Grays as light shades of black are associated with seriousness and sophistication in quantitative studies (Labrecque & Milne, 2013). Specific research has linked particular colors to certain functionalities that indicate serious thought. For example Lichtenfeld et al. have tied seeing the color green to improved performance on creative tasks via experiment-based research (2012). Integrating this research: use of colors such as a bright sage green is appropriate for a knowledge worker’s workspace; it will support the sort of mental state that leads to successful performance of complex cognitive tasks.

Paratelic state

Bold primary colors, such as a classic, pumpkin orange, are likely to support a paratelic state (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994; Labrecque & Milne, 2013). The saturation and brightness levels of these colors have been linked to higher energy levels and orange, for example, is also associated with unsophisticated fun.

Conformist state

Rigorous research establishes that using a currently popular, bright but not very saturated color choice for a space, such as yellow in a kitchen in the United States, can support a conformist state (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994; Anon., 2012). Using the common color for the space will make socially accepted rules of behavior in the area more compelling to space users (Labrecque & Milne, 2013).

Negativistic state

Empirical research focused on sporting events has linked seeing the color black with a negativistic-type state (Webster, Urland, & Correll, 2012).

Autic state

Seeing one’s own favorite color makes an autic-type state more probable according to careful research reported by Veitch (Veitch, 2012). Having preferred sensory experiences has been linked to positive moods; preferred colors are often tied to pleasant prior-life experiences and have the capacity to bring them top of mind.

Alloic state

Viewing a warm color makes being in an alloic state more likely (Mehta, Chae, Zhu, & Soman, 2012). Mehta and his team established via data collected in carefully designed experiments that looking at these shades was linked to a greater propensity to engage in philanthropic behavior.

Sympathy state

Seeing a blue surface is likely to induce a sympathy state, research suggests (Aslam, 2006; Labrecque & Milne, 2013). Worldwide, seeing the color blue has been linked by empirical investigations to trusting the thing or object presented in this color, either symbolically (e.g., in a logo) or concretely.

Mastery state

Viewing a red surface makes a mastery state more probable ("Stop on Red! The Effects of Color May Lie Deep in Evolution. . ." 2011). As reported in "Stop on Red," researchers Kralik, Khan, Levin and Dobson have linked seeing red to attempts to compete with others, for example.

One note of caution here: different researchers use motivational and emotional terms in different ways. It is therefore not sure, for example, that a word like 'energizing' is synonymous with 'arousing,' or 'trusting' the same as 'caring. So we should treat the relationships just outlined with some caution and use them as indications for further research. Ideally such research will make use of standard reversal theory psychometric scales, such as the Reversal Theory State Measure (Desselles, Murphy & Theys, 2014).

Conclusions

One final point here: Many buildings and rooms have multiple functions, and serve the needs of people in different motivational states. The need for this is emphasized by reversal theory. We need to develop straightforward ways to change the features of rooms to induce or sustain different states, e.g. furniture that can be easily rearranged, screens that can be repositioned/changed, alternative background colors that can be modified electronically, seats that can pivot from having one view to another, etc.

This paper has initiated the process of formalizing and systematizing the relationship between different design features and motivational states. We have illustrated this specifically by reference to doors and to surface colors. But of course, the theory relates in principle to every architectural feature and design variable. Reversal theory supplies a comprehensive structure to inform design decisions, one that can usefully be applied to a wide range of such decisions, from the selection of objects (e.g. ornaments) and furniture in rooms to the form of rooms and buildings themselves. Successful architects and designers no doubt already, intuitively, understand some of the kinds of relationships that have been discussed in this paper, but the aim here has been to start to lay the foundations of a more systematic and general study of the way that motivational states enter into the success or otherwise of particular objects and building.

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This is not a watch. Reframing the design of wrist-worn devices

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Abstract Various types of wrist-worn devices are increasingly introduced as consumer products in our daily life. However, most of these devices are framed as *a watch* regardless of their different purposes and contexts of use. This paper reflects on the design of current wrist-worn devices and reframes their meanings with an aim to inform and inspire further design explorations. We conducted a trend survey by reviewing articles about consumer wearable design and technology from popular online press and student design explorations. The insights from the trend survey and the design explorations are synthesized to identify gaps and overlaps between wearable design *in the wild* and *in a design studio context*. Based on the insights from both approaches, we propose varied meanings of wrist-worn devices in relation to corresponding formal and technological components. The meanings include 1) tracker for making sense of personal behaviors and situations, 2) controller for streamlining interactions across connected devices with unique affordance and style, 3) notification manager for prompting follow-up actions with minimal distraction, and 4) statement for lifestyle changes and goal achievement. Based on the proposed framework, further design and research implications are discussed toward connected and mediated human experience with augmented digital systems.

Keywords *Wearable devices, Wrist-worn devices, Forms, Meanings, Design-driven approaches*

Introduction

Forms and meanings of recent digital products have become diversified according to technological development and lifestyle changes. Digital devices are no longer limited to flat screen-based forms for supporting work-related tasks but expanded to flexible and embedded forms for assisting a wide range of personal activities including fitness, leisure and communication. Wearable is one of the largely emerging forms of digital devices, and new applications and systems under this category have been increasingly introduced, influencing on broader ecosystems of other digital devices and related services. Wrist-worn devices are one of the representative forms of wearable products today. While their potential in new user experiences and business opportunities seems to be promising, their design space has not been fully explored yet when it comes to their creative forms and meanings (Xu & Lyons, 2015). The market is saturated in a sense with too many similar types of devices—mostly in forms of fitness tracking wristbands or notice alerting smartwatches, and the marriage between technology and fashion in the design of these devices is still in its experimental stage, although its importance is being more seriously considered. The growing number of wrist worn digital devices brings back the battle between the traditional watch industry and the information technology industry from early 1980's,

raising tensions between electronic and mechanical components, and between technology-driven and craft-oriented approaches in watch design (Thompson, 2015).

Regardless of their growing number and technical capabilities, wrist wearable devices are still a new product category; and in most cases people do not know what to expect from them and what to use them for (Pizza, Brown, McMillan & Lampinen, 2016). There have been studies that investigate possible meanings, forms and use cases of wrist-worn digital devices based on familiar use cases of analogue watches (Lyons, 2015). Although such frame of watch may facilitate the design and use of new wearable devices with the reference of familiar forms and meanings, digital products could do far more and the semantic frame of wristband or smartwatch could limit creative approaches to wearable devices. In addition, the current design of wristbands or smartwatches is largely pushed by technology and market opportunities, not yet fully leveraging aesthetic and experiential potentials of wearable media and interaction technology (Pederson, 2013). We argue that there is a need for reflecting on trending issues about the design of wrist worn devices in order to speculate on yet-unexplored meanings and forms of these devices with greater impacts on user experience. This study, taking a critical stance to technology-driven

approaches to consumer wearable devices, reflects on their deeper meanings and purposes of use based on our survey of recent design trends and case studies of design explorations. By doing so, we aim to reconceptualize the design of wrist-worn devices and to propose a reflective framework, which could better inform and inspire design-driven explorations to this category of devices. Specific methods and objectives of this study follow in the next section.

Methods and objectives

This paper reflects on issues and approaches related to the design of wrist-worn devices with a focus on their meanings and forms. First, we conducted a trend survey by reviewing articles about wearable design, technology and business from popular online press in order to get a sense of what types of wrist-worn devices exist, how they are marketed, and which elements are involved in their design beyond form-making. In parallel, we also conducted student design explorations as studio projects to investigate detailed formal elements of and related design approaches to wearable applications, followed by a debrief session about the project outcomes and processes. The survey and design explorations were not planned to inform each other from the beginning. Instead of applying or proving insights from one to the other, we intended to compare “real world” issues about the design of wrist-worn devices in practice and “design-focused” issues that are directly related to concept development and form-making process. By conducting the two studies separately, we aim to identify gaps and overlaps between wearable design *in the wild* and *in a design studio context*. In the end, we synthesize the insights from the two studies to sort through challenges and opportunities in further design explorations of wrist worn devices in relation with other digital systems.

The insights from the trend survey and design explorations are summarized in the following sections, put in *an innovation matrix* in the end. The innovation matrix was devised by Verganti (2009) to map out a trajectory of various meanings of a category of products in relation to different technologies associated with each meaning. According to Verganti, product innovations happen in two dimensions: *development of new technology* (i.e., faster processing speed, smaller size, cheaper cost, efficient engineering solutions) and *discovery of new meanings* (i.e., product values, user experiences). He argues that the former is considered as engineering-driven innovation, while the later as truly design-driven innovation. The discovery of new meaning, supported by corresponding technology, expands design opportunities by adding new values to market and user experience, as seen in many design cases (e.g., Alessi Anna G. Corkscrew that shifted meanings of wine openers from a kitchen gadget to a playful artifact, Nintendo Wii remote controller with motion sensor that shifted meanings of video games from a computer graphical experience to a bodily experience). Later on, *radical innovation in meaning* is further discussed in Norman and Verganti (2014) as an alternative perspective to currently dominant User-Centered Design (UCD) approaches, which they argue

mostly result in *incremental improvements* of product features based on observed user needs or problems. Instead, radical innovation results from *technology epiphany* through the discovery of quiescent meanings as forward looking approach to design. Although the process is not as straightforward as incremental design improvement (that is grounded on structured user research or evaluation), technology epiphany does not come by chance either. It requires critical and rigorous design discourse by considering psychological and cultural dimensions of being human including values, beliefs, norms and traditions. The role of designers as *interpreter* is emphasized to synthesize all relevant issues and trends into deeper insights and to create *an object as a proposal* by envisioning new values.

As a foundation for such discovery and proposal of new meanings, in what follows, we map out technological and sociocultural issues revealed from our trend research and synthesize them with the insights from our design explorations. Under our main goal to reflect and reframe the design of wrist-worn devices, specific objectives of this paper include 1) investigating their meanings in broader product ecology, 2) identifying their form factors in relation to their meanings, and 3) speculating how design-driven approaches could come into the scene where many conflicting constraints coexist.

Survey of trending issues about wrist-worn devices

As an initial attempt to get a sense of existing products and relevant design issues in practice, we reviewed articles about wearable design published in technology, fashion, lifestyle and business magazines as well as design blogs (i.e., The Atlantic, The Economist, Fast Company, Wired, Fashion Nerd, Creative Applications, Mashable, Visual News) by subscribing them over 3 months (May – August, 2015), archiving the articles specific to “wearables” and further investigating products and projects mentioned in those articles. In addition, we looked into crowdfunding websites including Kickstarter and Indiegogo to take new start-up projects into account, and also attended Wearable Technologies Conference (July 9-10 2015 in San Francisco), which hosted wearable product showcases, platform/solution demonstrations, and panel discussions on facing issues in wearable industry. From all these sources, related design cases that share similar technology or business issues are selected and categorized into trends. In what follows, four selected trends are highlighted, each of which corresponds to different meanings and formal and technological components of wrist-worn devices.

Trending issue 1: activity and/or mood tracker

Thanks to advanced information and sensor technology, tracking and monitoring personal data has become widely available as consumer wearable devices. Fitness trackers are one of the most popular forms of wearable devices today. Their meanings and functions are largely grounded on the notion of *quantified self*, which views a personal life as an integral of quantitatively measurable activities (The

Economist, 2013). Beyond tracking activities in real time, the notion is expanded to prompt self-reflection on accumulated patterns or noticeable changes of personal behaviors over time, enabling individuals to better know about themselves and even to experiment with different personal strategies in managing their life activities. With common technical features of tracking movement (e.g., steps, postures) or health condition (e.g., heart rate), product meanings could vary depending on different marketing strategies and intended experiential values, ranging from *activity tracker* or *health monitor* (e.g., Fitbit) to *fitness companion* or *personal coach* (e.g., MOOV: multi-sport wearable coach) as well as to *mood tracker* (e.g., Sona: bracelet for mind and body wellness, Embrace Watch: stress monitoring watch, myfeel: wristband that recognizes emotions). We have observed that attempts are increasing to infer mood or emotional conditions by synthesizing activity, physiological and contextual data and manual logs.

While compact size and minimal interface design (both in terms of inputs and displays) are general design considerations for such tracking devices, variations of materials and unique styles are experimented as a point of difference based on the brand strategy of each device. In addition, there are immense design opportunities being discussed for mobile apps, which work in connection with wrist-worn tracking devices. Mobile apps play a crucial role in guiding self-reflection through simple visualizations of behavioral patterns and streamlined interactions for achieving goals with engaging visual incentives based on cognitive behavioral therapy.

Trending issue 2: smartwatch

The design of wrist-worn devices needs to be understood in the context of digital ecosystems where multiple devices—including mobile phones, consumer and home electronic devices, and automotive devices—cooperatively interact with each other by sharing information and functionality across them (Levy, 2015). Within complex digital ecosystems, devices serve as a set of *endpoints* to access applications and information archived in the cloud or to interact with people, social communities and businesses beyond the scope of personal activities. Personal, social and environmental data captured through the device mesh will construct dynamic digital information ecosystems and model users' behavior journeys to facilitate the delivery of apps and services according to their contexts. Smartwatch, one of the representative types of wearable devices, serves as a platform for quickly accessing, managing and updating information from other devices, involving with more active and complex interactions than passive trackers to navigate through different apps and information states built in them. Unique forms and affordances of interfaces for specific tasks could be sacrificed to accommodate different purposes in one device. A wrist has become an even more rare estate for wearable devices due to the competition between versatile smartwatches and single-purpose devices.

Meanings of smartwatches and purposes for using them are multifaceted compared to those of single-

purpose activity trackers due to their versatile features and use cases. A recent study reports that Apple Watch since released in 2015 has been mostly used to check *time*, *activity data*, and *notifications* (Pizza, Brown, McMillan & Lampinen, 2016). Although these main uses are not surprising or exciting, the study discusses implications about deeper meanings behind checking time and activity records in terms of proactive personal schedule or goal management. Checking notifications is considered as *triage* of incoming messages or emails from other devices to reduce their interruptions in other foreground tasks. With increasing technology capabilities and broadening application areas, the meanings of smartwatches are evolving to be more deeply involved in our daily routines, reshaping broader ecosystems of digital and physical devices (Bernaerts et al., 2015).

Trending issue 3: fashionable tech

With their increasing capabilities and intimacy, wearable devices nowadays do not only serve as utilitarian artifacts but also display their sociocultural values and personal tastes as fashion items. However, regardless of the growing use of fitness trackers or smartwatches, still they are rather considered as digital gadgets than fashion accessories, not experienced as part of a complete outfit (Kessler, 2015). Styles and aesthetic expressions are as critical considerations as technical features and usability in the design and use of wearable devices. Different design approaches and inspirations are searched for from fashion studies to complement current digital product design where user-centered approaches are dominant (Pan and Stolterman, 2015). On the contrary to such utilitarian, problem-driven design approaches, fashion design is driven by continuous changes and possibilities, intentionally creating new values and variations, reflecting (and often leading) emerging lifestyles (Juhlin, 2015). In this regard, sociocultural perspectives of styles and economic values of materials are also important design factors to consider in addition to technical and functional features of wearable devices, and wearable design requires truly multi-disciplinary expertise and methodology more than any other consumer product categories (Raj & Ha-Brookshire, 2015). The marriage between fashion and technology is constantly experimented in practice through collaborations between high-end fashion brands and/or designers and information technology companies, for example, by applying new styles or materials to the exterior of digital devices (e.g., Apple Watch Hermès) or by embedding technical features into fashion and jewelry that are already a big part of our life (e.g., making payments with clothing introduced by Friedman, 2015; illuminated uniform for communication among flight crew introduced by Pakhchyan, 2015). These fashion-driven approaches are radical in a sense that they turn down the mantra of form follows function in modern product design by putting function into seemingly irrelevant forms of existing artifacts. Through radical approaches to digital product design, current forms of digital devices, which consist of discrete input and display interfaces, could be further *deconstructed* and *realigned* into new interactive experience embedded in fashion.

Trending issue 4: creative and critical exploration

Besides already widely used consumer products, new concepts for wrist-worn devices are continuously introduced by start-ups, research labs and creative individuals, proposing new meanings and forms for wrist-worn devices with new device features and shapes (e.g., Kapture: audio recording wristband that looks like a retro microphone), band and display materials (e.g., analogue activity tracker that employs insoluble liquids as display materials, designed by Vanhemert, 2015), display interfaces (e.g., smartwatch display customized to visualize football match results, introduced in Cool Wearable, 2014), and multi-sensory interactions (e.g., Doppel - pace setting wristband through vibration; Arduino wearable prototypes introduced in Einarson, 2013; Ahn et al, 2015). Thanks to more accessible prototyping technologies including 3D printer and electronic circuit printer as well as popularized social platforms for crowdfunding, it has become relatively easier to turn ideas into prototypes. However, the translation from a prototype to a product is still challenging due to too many competitors, social and government regulations in health data tracking and interventions, and common technical constraints in terms of battery or platform for device network, most of which are not necessarily direct design problems from a particular perspective concerning on forms and meanings. Although technical constraints and regulations in the real world should not be ignored in design, at least sorting through which factors could be further explored from a design-oriented approach would shed light on more meaningful areas for future design research and education. Recently there are increasing creative and critical initiatives in design research to envision the future of technology and human life by provoking and reframing problems beyond solving given ones: for example, as seen in the notions of *slow technology* that promotes the use of technology for reflection (vs. for productivity) (Hallnäs & Redström, 2011), *grounded innovation* that experiments applications of new technology by developing unique use cases with marginalized or pioneering user groups (Holmquist, 2012), *concept-driven interaction* design that proposes a theoretically and historically grounded approach to develop innovative design concepts (Stolterman & Wiberg, 2010), and *speculative design* that brings fiction as a means of provoking social visions (Dunne & Raby, 2013). These alternative approaches for creative and critical design explorations are also in demand to support design-driven innovation in wearable design.

Showcase of design explorations from studio projects

This section describes our design explorations conducted as two studio courses in the School of Design at University of Cincinnati: one with seniors (Fall, 2014) and the other with first year masters (Spring, 2014). Both studios aimed to explore unique forms and meanings of wearable devices based on research, use case development and iterative prototyping. Research activities included survey of emerging social, cultural and technology trends as well as literature review and primary research about

chosen user groups and contexts. In terms of prototyping, paper and foam board mock-ups were employed at earlier phases; 3D renderings and screen mockups were mostly used to specify formal details; and electronic prototyping with Arduino was also used optionally to test conceptual or technical feasibility of proposed concepts. While the senior studio focused on formal development and refinement for branding and manufacturing details, the graduate studio emphasized conceptual explorations of speculative wearable systems.

The senior studio was carried out as an interdisciplinary design course with 18 enrolled students from industrial, communication and fashion design programs across 15 weeks. Students collaboratively conducted trend research about emerging technology and social issues to identify particular situations where wearable technology could be introduced with promising opportunities, and explored unique forms to address and/or resolve their focused design problems. The project brief did not specify to design wrist-worn devices, but three out of five team projects in total were turned out to be wrist wearable (Figure 1: Echo, Figure 2: Audapt, Figure 4: Cue) with one glove type device (Figure 5: Gro) and one clip type device for bike signaling.

The graduate course was carried out as independent studio projects across 15 weeks with 6 students, all of whom have their background in industrial or communication design. Students conducted literature review about contemporary communication culture with wearable media technology, and each took on a concept for individual project to leverage experiential potentials of embodied digital media. One project out of five in total was turned out to be wrist wearable (Figure 3: Squeezing Bracelet) with the other four were presented as conceptual systems connected and embedded in other objects or environments (Figure 6 – 8: smart shoes, spikey mobile phone cover, alarming pillow, haptic GPS navigation gloves, and gaming t-shirt).

In what follows, we introduce three selected projects of wrist-worn devices to showcase their design processes in terms of how detail form factors and interfaces have been explored and integrated with specific use cases.

Project 1. Echo: the modern yodel

Echo is a communication device for snowboarders, who need to navigate and connect to remotely located team members on the mountain. To resolve their hassles of taking out a mobile phone from their pocket and manipulating its touch screen with their fingers out of gloves, it proposes a *rotate-and-press* interface solution, which is integrated into the physical frame around the digital screen, making it easy to manipulate by holding and pressing the frame still with their gloves on their hands. The screen interface and navigation are simplified to accommodate the rotate-and-press manipulation with the frame. The frame does not only solve the concerned problem in use, but also adds a bold and bulky style to the device, which properly communicates its intended use.

Figure 1. Echo with rotate-and-press interface (Design by Mitch Bernarding, Jennifer Beruscha, Seth Gilgipse and Katarina Jung).

Figure 2. Audapt with swipe-and-tap interface (Design by Jay Jansen, Jon Riehle, Julie Morycz and Trent Victor).

Project 2. Audapt: the hearing controller

Audapt is a hearing aid system that consists of a hearing aid piece, a mobile app, and a wrist-worn controller. Hearing aids are usually hard to adjust, uncomfortable, and carry a stigma with their often-unsightly appearance. To make them easy to control and fashionable, a mobile app and a wrist controller are proposed as primary and secondary controllers. The four lights on the wrist controller correspond to four hearing presets customized in the mobile app, and can be switched by swiping left and right on the indented interface of the device. Tapping each end of the interface module adjusts volume. This interface solution was detailed after iterative sketches of different display face shapes and arrangements of input and output interfaces, most of which quite looked like a regular watch. It has been a main design issue for this team to make the device *not-looking-like-watch*, and they came up with a simpler interface solution than regular watch faces by integrating inputs and outputs with minimal hints of visual affordance for swiping and tapping and display lights.

Project 3. Squeezing bracelet

Squeezing bracelet is a conceptual wearable device that reminds of tasks to be completed in connection with a scheduler mobile app. Five tasks can be added to a daily to-do list with specific due times set in the mobile app, and each task is represented in distinct lights on the bracelet. If a task is not checked out by its due time, the bracelet will give a reminder by blinking its corresponding light and being continuously squeezed as time passes. The concept is rather a critical statement than a practical solution by expressing our obsession with productivity through its unpleasant look-and-feel like a handcuff and corresponding physical punishment.

Debrief of design processes and outcomes

In addition to regular studio critique sessions and observations throughout these design explorations, a focus group was conducted with four volunteering students to debrief design processes and outcomes. Although not all concepts proposed from the design exploration are conceptually or technically innovative,

Figure 3. Squeezing Bracelet: sketch and rendered images (Design by Soojin Kim).

Figure 4. Cue: modular clip for managing notifications (Design by Kyle Bennett, Minsun Hong, Chelsey Burgess and Tom Pietzsch).

each of the projects showcases a unique form-making process by illustrating how detail form factors and interface solutions are explored and integrated with specific meanings of their use cases. One of the frequently mentioned challenges in the form explorations was to make a wrist-worn device *not looking like a watch*. Just because of the basic formal structure consisting of a display face and a band, their designed device was easily considered as a watch during critiques, and thus their intended design problems and solutions were not successfully communicated at the beginning. Focusing on particular problems and interactive tasks helped them *deconstruct* the watch structure and come up with simple but unique interface forms. At the same time, a compact device size was definitely a critical constraint in exploring diverse formal structures and integrating complex interactive features. However, as most design solutions were developed in connection with mobile apps, the problem with limited interface and display surface was partly resolved by using larger screen of smartphones. The pair of a wrist-worn device and a mobile app has become a common product system with the wrist-worn device in charge of passive data tracking and quick access to selected features and the app in charge of complex information visualization and navigation. Lastly, some interactive aspects of proposed concepts were experimented in electronic prototyping by using Arduino in order to test their conceptual and technical validity, for example, in the case of Squeezing Bracelet, a tightening structure was tested with a micro motor controlled by a mobile app

via Bluetooth. However, it was challenging to demonstrate such wireless communication between multiple devices compared to its reward in terms of exploration and evaluation of initial concepts. Too much technical knowledge and experiments were required for designers without engineering background to demonstrate a customized pairing of multiple devices, while using a ready-made toolkit is limiting design explorations. In spite of this challenge, interactive prototyping was still helpful to *experience* a proposed design scenario, especially to simulate initial interaction flows of embedded systems where tangible or visible formal elements are not clear.

There are also other forms of wearable devices explored beside wrist-wearables, including a modular clip for displaying notifications from a smartphone (Figure 4: Cue), a lighting module for bikers to communicate turn signals with hand gestures, a gardening glove that measures soil conditions for beginners (Figure 5: Gro), haptic GPS navigation gloves (Figure 6: JA), a spiky mobile phone cover that prevents it from being held or used in bedtime (Figure 7), an alarm pillow that vibrates in the morning, vibrating shoes that encourage working out, a t-shirt for playing a mobile phone game by sending vibration messages through a wirelessly connected t-shirt (Figure 8: Salmon). These different forms of design concepts still illustrate a common user expectation for interactive applications that goes beyond wearable forms by connecting various digital or physical objects to assist human activities and augment human

Figure 5. Gro: smart gardening glove for on-site soil testing and recording (Design by El-Asa Crawford, Jacklyn Crofts and Shirley Yip).

Figure 6. JA: haptic GPS navigation gloves (Design by Soojin Kim).

Figure 7. A spiky mobile phone cover that prevents it from being held at night (Design by Yanhan Li).

Figure 8. Salmon: vibrating t-shirt connected to a mobile game (Design by Bennett Nestok and Patrick Fitzgerald).

abilities through *proactive data tracking* and its *proper representation*, which will be further discussed in the next section.

Reflection: if not a watch, then what is it?

The selected design cases above illustrate how particular needs or problems identified from research have been resolved in unique forms of interfaces through systematic formal explorations. Different parts of wrist-worn devices (e.g., displays—either visual or tactile, frames around display faces, bands, and other peripheral devices) could be developed or combined into new formal structures, interface components, and aesthetic styles. Regarding our initial argument about the need for alternative conceptual frames of wrist-worn devices, we reflect on what else they could mean by deconstructing their functional and experiential design elements. In the innovation matrix (Table 1), the four meanings emerged from our trend survey and design explorations are listed on the x-axis and mapped to related technological components on the y-axis,

constructing varied conceptual frames described below. The proposed frames are by no means mutually exclusive or definitive. Instead, they are meant to be continuously expanded and combined through further design explorations.

Frame 1: Tracker for making sense of personal behaviors and situations

As reviewed in the trend survey, diverse human activities can be tracked with more compact but accurate sensors, and the interpretation and representation of tracked data has become a significant design concern to guide self-reflection through engaging interaction prompts (Sanches, 2000). While tracking technology and relevant studies about quantified self have opened up a new design space for personal fitness and health management through wearable devices (Wallack 2015), it should be noted that not all human activities are quantifiable; trackable data represents only part of human life; and too much data could add more cognitive fatigue, if not properly synthesized (Bumgardner, 2015; Wagstaff,

2015). More complex factors are involved in a personal life including social, emotional and environmental conditions beyond physical activities. Especially emotional awareness has become a more important subject in the contemporary society with increasing cognitive load from digital devices and various information sources, and commercial interest and technological capabilities for emotional tracking and mood changing are further growing. However, this area has been rarely approached in our studio projects, and our assumption is: as such design opportunities largely rely on data analytics, it was hard to develop new concepts of data tracking and synthesis without already collected set of data or proper design tools to play with it. Not only passive tracking, but also proactive user reflections on their tracked behavioral data need to be considered as a whole cycle of user experience, and corresponding theoretical and technical support is in need for design explorations. In addition, creative interpretations of bodily interactions beyond counting steps or tracking locations could be further explored in relation to their effects on our physical and social life (Johnson, 2008; Höök et al., 2015). Specifically, the concept of *lived body*, the interconnected relationships between human perception and action in physical and social context (Svanæs, 2013), could be expanded with connected data tracking system to make better sense of our environment as well as to make optimal decisions for actions with less cognitive effort (Dijk, Lugt & Hummels, 2014).

Frame 2: Controller for streamlining interaction with unique affordance and style

As evident both in the trend related to smartwatches and our design explorations, most wrist-worn devices are used as a secondary controller to quickly access selected features or data from other devices connected within digital ecosystems. Thanks to the development of short-range, ad hoc networking technologies, a digital ecosystem could be more fluidly expanded and assembled with multiple devices (Jung et al. 2010), and a mobile app usually serves as a default platform to set up and navigate complex information in

connection with a wrist-worn device. Design opportunities in this frame have been most actively explored in our design projects, especially in terms of developing unique forms, styles and interfaces of wrist-worn devices. While the design of wrist-worn controllers is supposed to be simple and minimal in terms of their forms, they also should correspond to the interaction flow and navigation hierarchy of other devices and applications connected within their system in order to support streamlined user experience across them. Specifically, types of information, related interaction tasks, and navigation structure behind a controller device should be carefully crafted into proper interface forms to represent their affordance and ergonomics. As seen in the cases of Echo and Audapt, successful interface solutions of a simple controller could potentially become an iconic style of its product system, and could distinguish a particular wrist-worn device from regular watches both by look and functionality.

Frame 3: Notification center for prompting actions with minimal distraction

Although wrist-worn devices could do and mean more than a watch, the watch analogy has been still valid in many of our graduate design explorations by viewing time as a critical experiential factor of these devices that give a reminder or prompt a user of what to do. Back to the point addressed in our focus group, as interactive systems become more pervasive and ubiquitous in our life, people more and more expect for such systems to be seamlessly weaved into their temporal and spatial context by autonomously tracking time spent on certain tasks, reminding them of what to do at a certain time, assessing their time management, and so on. The expectation is being further raised for devices to recommend a user what to do and guide him/her to do desired behaviors based on the understanding of his/her routine. Beside algorithmic approaches to such reminder or recommendation features, more persuasive and engaging forms of interventions could be explored with different materials and sensory modes of interactions (Juhlin, Zhang, Sundbom and Fernaeus,

Table 1. Innovation Matrix: mapping various meanings and technologies associated with wrist-worn devices.

2013) with minimal interruptions in foreground user activities. Beyond blindly satisfying somewhat of productivity-obsessed expectations, critical design perspectives and corresponding design cases are also in demand to speculate on healthier human-device relationships and their symbiotic interactions, as in the case of Squeezing Bracelet.

Frame 4: Statement for lifestyle changes and goal achievement

Beyond their functional features, wearable devices are also marketed as fashion items that display one's lifestyle, communities involved and values aspired to. The act of wearing an interactive device partly expresses one's personal statement that the wearer has a certain intention (e.g., fitness tracking, health monitoring, time management) and s/he is committed to it. Especially, by wearing a tracker or reminder device, a wearer is not only informed of their behavior patterns by the device, but also influenced by his/her commitment represented by the device. In addition, social recognition of the user's intention through the device could lead to support from others. Related design implications could be further discussed in terms of persuasive technology, fashion, and emotional attachment to a wearable device, opening up more design opportunities toward personalized meanings and interactions of wearable devices (Tsaknaki, Fernaeus and Jonsson, 2015) and social communities augmented by wearable systems (Kortuem and Segall, 2003). Such emphasis on personal values and community support enabled by wearable technologies could empower individuals to better understand who they are and what they aspire to based on informed self-awareness, guided self-reflection and connected support, thus to make impactful changes in their life and society.

Conclusion

This paper reflected on the forms and meanings of wrist-worn devices based on the review of trending issues about current wrist-worn products and our design explorations conducted as student projects. The insights from the trend survey and the design explorations are compared to identify gaps and overlaps between wearable design in the wild and in a design studio. The reflection is led to propose nuanced conceptual frames by making connections between various experiential and functional values and formal and technological components of wrist-worn devices. Our contribution lies in deconstructing mixed meanings and functional elements of wrist-worn devices, which were mostly imposed by traditional watches, and realigning them into a reflective design framework. In doing so, we also highlight challenges and opportunities for exploring new forms and meanings of wrist-worn devices that could support connected and mediated human experience with augmented digital systems. We expect the proposed framework could serve as a foundation for future design explorations by connecting wearable design study and practice and that the framework could be further expanded and consolidated by more exploratory design cases.

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Attributes of positive user experience and the relation to product type and time

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Abstract Since user-centered design came to the forefront, user research has been treated as almost essential in product development process but utilized in limitation in spite of its importance. This is because traditional user study methods are time-consuming. Therefore, this study attempts to make an empirical interaction model, User Experience Attributes (UXA) in which how user experience with product or service interacts with product type and usage stage is shown. To achieve this goal, we firstly redefined attributes of positive user experience through literature review. Five attributes of positive user experience were created: sensory, instrumental, episodic, value and symbolic experiences. A mobile-based questionnaire was developed to figure out what kind of products are related to positive user experience, why they loved the product, and how positive user experience changed over time. 102 respondents participated in the survey. The results indicate that the importance of five attributes varied depending upon product type and product usage stage. The findings from the study provide an empirical interaction model showing the relation between positive user experiences, product type and usage stage with design practitioners. If it is considered in the product development process, it could reduce time and cost compared with traditional user study methods.

Keywords *User experience, Product type, Usage stage, User-centered design*

Introduction

Since user-centered design came to the forefront, user research has been treated as almost essential in product development process but utilized in limitation in spite of its importance (Lew, 2011). This situation is due to the limitations that user study methods have: 1) traditional user research methods require too much time and resources to prepare, conduct and analyze, and 2) users' needs and wishes identified from several studies cannot actually cover all the different kinds of users considering their characteristics and background knowledge (Kramer, Noronha, & Vergo, 2000; Spinuzzi, 2005). Since market is rapidly changing nowadays, those limitations are more and more critical to design practitioners. As a result, it is very challenging to carry out in-depth user research with existing user research methods. Considering these circumstances, we believe that an empirical interaction model showing how products (or services) interact with users could help design practitioners easily cope with volatile market situations instead of time-consuming and costly traditional user research.

As a try of creating an empirical model, an empirical model in our previous study (Kim & Christiaans, 2012; Kim, 2014) was developed. The focus was on the interaction between user characteristics, product types and negative product experience. The study revealed that negative user experience results mostly from the lack of instrumental value of a product and also negative user experience is rather universal

among people less depending on user characteristics. From the findings only it was not possible to draw a holistic picture of the relationship between product type, user characteristics and user experience. Considering the characteristics of positive product experience (i.e. the reasons people love to use their product), it seems that not only instrumental value but also aesthetic, personal and social values play an important role. In addition to that, usage period of product may influence positive user experience because product attachment is somehow influenced by time (Karapanos, Zimmerman, Forlizzi, & Martens, 2010). Therefore, this study as the first step to complete a holistic picture of user experience aims to 1) redefine positive user experience, 2) to empirically investigate how positive user experiences are related to product type in terms of the redefined user experience, and 3) to explore the influence of product usage period to positive user experience.

What is user experience?

One of the field that the concept of user experience or user-centered design was firstly introduced was human-computer interaction. According to Moggridge (2007), thanks to researchers' effort for ordinary people to use digital technology easier, nowadays' user can control their devices friendly without professional knowledge about programming (as cited in Wright & McCarthy, 2010). Those efforts about user-centered design were soon become a concept focusing on not just usability of technologies but how the users have

good experience (Wright & McCarthy, 2010), but the question was how the good experience could be made.

Hassenzahl (2008) tried to find the origins of UX at the level of personal achievement, and there are two kinds of personal achievements: 'do-goals' and 'be-goals'. Do-goals (pragmatic quality) facilitates fulfillment of be-goals (hedonic goals), and those hedonic attributes hold the key of experience. Consequently, he defined good UX as a result of fulfilled human needs, which are required to achieve be-goals: being autonomous, competent, related to other, simulated and popular.

Although user experience has been defined by International Standard Organization as "person's perceptions and responses resulting from the use and/or anticipated use of a product, system or service," (2010) attributes of user experience have been differently understood among disciplines because each one has their own perception on the term. For instance, Rafaeli and Vinal-Yavets (2004), an ergonomist and behavioral psychologist, suggested three components of user experience as *Instrumentality*, *Aesthetics*, and *Symbolism* of an artifact. Desmet (2007), a design researcher, classified product experience as *Aesthetic Experience*, *Attribution of Meaning* and *Emotional Experience*. Those two categorizations are similar in a sense that both emphasized experiences of aesthetics and meaning. However, in the former it stands for associational meaning, symbolic meaning attributed by relationship with others, while in the latter it is more about personal attachments to product. *Emotional Experience* in Desmet's classification stands for emotional assessment by a user, and it can be made without user's awareness. Comparing to Rafaeli's study which focused on the elements arousing user experiences, Desmet's study had their point on types of consequential experiences, thus Desmet classified *emotional response* as independent type of user experience. On the other hand, *Instrumentality* is a type of human-product interaction in Desmet's study, whereas Rafaeli classified it as one of the dimensions that makes product experience of the user.

In the field of psychology, Jordan (1999) attempted to consider positive user experience as pleasure. According to his theory, pleasure is caused by operation of sensory organs (*Physio-pleasure*), social interaction (*Socio-pleasure*), cognitive issues (*Psycho-pleasure*), and personal aspiration (*Ideo-pleasure*). Hassenzahl (2003), designer and applied psychologist, however, distinguished user experience in terms of two perspectives based on people's quality perceptions: *pragmatic* and *hedonic*. Pragmatic attribute regards instrumental goal of products, and hedonic attribute considers users' psychological goodness. The two categories are not exactly matched with Jordan's classification, but Jordan's model tends to focus more on interactions between human and product, whereas Hassenzahl's focus is on psychological or emotional functions of products.

In another study of Hassenzahl (2006), he suggested a broader framework about facets of user experience,

and it contained not only the relationship of pragmatic-hedonic needs, but emotion and experiential aspects. He highlighted the importance of emotion in terms of experience and pointed out that designer should consider the context of emotion rather than emotion itself. In addition to that, situational and temporal background, thus experiential aspect, also help to control affective state of users according to him.

Low (2006) introduced six attributes of product character called PCA (Product Character Attributes), which comprises *Aesthetics*, *Function*, *Symbolism*, *Sexuality*, *Experiences*, and *Mediation*. *Mediation* is an attribute about associating with other people, so common understanding or relationship on a product can be categorized into this attribute. According to the paper, *Experience* also counted as an attribute, and it is aroused from cognitive and emotional traits of a product, similarly with *Psycho-pleasure* or *Emotional experience*. The concept of *Aesthetics* is similar with ones of Desmet's and Rafaeli's, or *Physio-pleasure* of Jordan's study. While *Instrumentality* in Rafaeli's study is focusing on how a product promote its goal or support users' achievement, the concept of *Function* in Low's study just matters fulfillment of user needs. *Symbolism* refers representative metaphor or primary traits of a product, so it is quite different from the *Meaning* of Desmet's study. However, *Symbolism* of Rafaeli's study can include not only *Symbolism* of Low's concept, but also *Sexuality*, which means sexual identity or personality of product.

Redefined user experience

In order to redefine dimensions of user experience based on the existing models, an affinity diagram analysis was conducted. This analysis was done with a doctoral researcher, two master students, and three undergraduate students in design major.

Components that had similarities in subjects of manifesting experiences or types of interactions were grouped together, then the groups were defined the following characteristics of its components: sensory experience, instrumental experience, episodic experience, value experience and symbolic experience (see Figure 1). This new categorization of user experience does not mean that all user experiences can be clearly distinguished and divided. Rather, they mean characteristics that cause experiences with products or services.

This model is named as User eXperience Attributes (UXA, acronymically) *and the description of each attribute is as follows:*

Instrumental experience is evoked from the experience from how easily an instrumental goal is achieved that users expect while using a product. The instrumental experience is closely associated with usability, efficiency, convenience, functionality, and practicality.

Sensory experience means, in process of using a product, experience resulting from sensorial quality that perceived by human senses. This attribute includes not only the perception of visual aesthetic

Figure 1. Comparison diagram between the existing models' and redefined user experience attributes.

but also all the sensorial perception such as auditory, tactile, olfactory, and gustatory senses.

Episodic experience refers to personal experience related to the user's memory or episode with a product. With episodic experience, a product plays a medium role in bridging between a memory or episode (e.g. a birthday gift from my boyfriend) and the user.

Value experience means experience made as a product provides a user with either values that are important to the user or values that are commonly accepted by the society the user belongs to. In other words, a user judges a product in a way how well the product meets his/her personal values or the values of the society they grew up.

Symbolic experience is generated from symbol or representation that a product socially stands for. It refers to experience that a user has when a product delivers the user to a social status or a social representation by the ownership of the product and consuming the brand of the product.

As described in the introduction, the focus was on positive user experiences since in our previous studies it was only instrumental experience that influenced negative user experiences in most cases (Kim & Christiaans, 2012). Therefore, this study empirically investigated 1) why people have positive experiences with a particular product (or service), and then identified 2) how the positive user experiences are related to the UX model. Furthermore, the study also tried to figure out 3) how the period of product usage is related to the attributes of positive user experience because time is a key factor to influence user experience (Hassenzahl & Ullrich, 2007; Karapanos et al., 2010; von Wilamowitz Moellendorff, Hassenzahl, Platz, & Wilamowitz-Moellendorff, 2006).

Method

In order to identify how the attributes of positive user experience are related to particular types of product and to figure out the interaction between the attributes and usage period of product, a mobile-based questionnaire survey was conducted.

Materials

A mobile-based questionnaire was developed to answer the research questions. Mobile-based questionnaire is useful to collect a number of data quickly within a limited period because it provides respondents with easy access through laptop computer or mobile phone. It consisted of three parts: usage period and UX, product type and UX, and Demographical information of respondent. The first part aimed to identify the relationship between the period of product usage and UX. For this, a question was formulated, how much they have experienced the product or service in terms of product lifecycle model (Cathy, 2014). Based on the model, each stage of product usage was modified into a statement to help respondent understand the question as below:

- *Unpacking: I just take the product off from its package.*
- *First use: I began to use the product or service.*
- *Ongoing use Phase 1: I am getting familiar with the product or service.*
- *Ongoing use Phase 2: I already got familiar with using this product or service.*
- *Discard/Replacement: now I am considering the product to be changed or discarded.*

The second part was for figuring out whether UXs are related to particular product types. Questions were made to ask the participants how much they agree on each of five attributes regarding the product they already mentioned in the previous question, and they were measured on five-level Likert scale. In order to make respondents better understood the notions of the attributes, detailed descriptions with relevant

examples were given before each question. For the attributes of which the given score was equal or more than '3(Neither of agree nor disagree)', an additional open-ended question was given asking why he/she had given the score. Then a question was lastly added to identify what attribute was most important among five attributes of positive product experience. After completing the questionnaire, a page asking demographical information of the respondent such as gender and age was shown.

Sample

In order to recruit as many respondents as possible, the survey was advertised through social networking services such as Facebook. A total of 102 respondents (50 males and 52 females) participated in the survey. They were all Koreans whose ages ranged from 15 to 56 years old ($M=31.47$, $SD=12.63$). 51 respondents out of 102 respondents were students, and the others were from diverse occupations such as administration officer, service provider, researchers and education provider.

Procedure

The questionnaire survey was conducted through an online platform which is called Typeform. The respondents were asked to first answer what his/her favorite product (or service). In the next page, they were asked to read each question regarding the five UXAs and mark on the five Likert scale (Strongly disagree, disagree, neither of agree nor disagree, agree, and Strongly Agree) how much they like the product because of that particular attribute. Except for the cases their mark was negative (below neutral, 3) for a certain attribute, they were asked to explain why she/he likes the product or service in details. After these questions, the respondents selected one of the five attributes, which was most important in explaining why he/she likes the product (or service).

Data analysis

Three types of data were gathered from the mobile-based questionnaire survey: the most favorite products or services, scores of each UXA on Likert scale, the most important attributes and descriptive data on the reasons they love the products or services.

All the products or services reported from the survey were grouped into 13 product categories: home appliances, consumer electronics, computer accessories, automotive products, stationaries, foods, infant products, sport products, clothes, cosmetics/beauty, home/decorations, health care products, and services. The product classification was made based on the categorization system of the biggest online shopping malls such as Amazon and EBay. Although services did not exist in the category systems of the shopping malls, it was added because service was also often reported in the survey as something the respondents liked to experience.

The scores of each UXA were averaged, and then the mean values were compared between product types as well as between the stages of usage. The most important attribute for each product type was quantitatively analyzed and its frequency was also

4 → How much have you used the product? ([Product Name])*

Following options are about stages of usage from your Purchase to Discard. Please answer what stage you are in, so far.

- A I just take the product off from its package.
- B I began to use the product or service.
- C I am getting familiar with the product or service.
- D I already got familiar with using this product or service.
- E Now I am considering the product to be changed or discarded.

Measuring Stage of Usage

5 → I like [Product Name], because of its sensory characteristics such as shape, sound, texture or touch.*

For examples:

- I like the shape and color of it.
- I am interested in the sound the product makes.
- The product gives me warm and soft feelings.

Scoring each attribute

(in case the score is 3 or higher)

11 → Please choose the most important reason why you like [Product Name].*

- A Value attributes: missions, social norms, shared values, faith or others.
- B Sensory attributes: shape, sound, touch or others.
- C Episodic attributes: memory, episodes, experiences, or others.
- D Instrumental attributes: functionality, efficiency, usability or others.
- E Symbolic attributes: brand, images, symbol, or others.
- F Other

Ranking the attributes

Figure 2. A part of the questionnaire measuring UXA.

considered in the analysis. Based on the descriptive data which contained information about why the respondents loved the products or services, sub-categories of each UXA were created by sorting in terms of similarity. Not only the most important attributes but also the other ones were taken into account to create the sub-categories of UXAs. This analysis was conducted by six undergraduate students who majored in industrial design, a master student and a doctoral researcher.

Results

Product type and positive user experience

A total of 102 products and services were reported as the most favorites and they were categorized into one of 13 product groups (Figure 3). Consumer electronics such as tablet PC, personal sound system and digital camera were most often mentioned (27%) and services

Figure 3. Percentages of The Most Favorite Products or Services in terms of product type (N=102).

and cosmetics were the second (16% respectively). The other categories took similar percentages ranging from 5% to 8%: sports (8%), computer accessories (8%), home appliances (7%), Home/decorations (6%), stationaries (5%). Others (7%) included health care product, automotive product, foods, infant products, and clothes. Product categories that had taken less than five percent were excluded in the further analysis because it would make the results biased with only a few cases.

Table 1. Positive user experience attributes and their subcategories.

User Experience Attribute	Coding	Sub-category
Sensory Experience	SE1	Perceived appearance
	SE2	Amusement in interactions
	SE3	Atmosphere/impression
	SE4	Sensorial comfort
Instrumental Experience	IE1	High functionality
	IE2	High durability
	IE3	Simplicity
	IE4	Efficiency
Episodic Experience	EE1	Gift
	EE2	Product (or service)-related episode
	EE3	Cumulated experiences
	EE4	Experience of problem solving
Value Experience	VE1	Self-administration/self-improvement
	VE2	Personal value
	VE3	Common benefit
Symbolic Experience	SyE1	Social recognition
	SyE2	Brand image or identity
	SyE3	Brand credibility
	SyE4	Sense of belonging

Sub-categories of positive user experience attributes

In consequence of clustering reasons why the respondents had positive user experiences with their product or service within each attribute, a total of 20 subcategories (four subcategories per attribute) were created as shown in Table 1. Each element of UXa somehow depends on each other rather than works independently to the overall outcome of user experience. Especially, last three attributes, Episodic experience, Value experience, and Social symbol experience could be the case in a sense that those attributes are more context-dependent than the others. Sensory, instrumental, episodic, value, and symbolic experience had each 69, 87, 39, 29 and 43 descriptive reasoning data.

Sensory Experience (see examples in Figure 4)

- **Perceived appearance (SE1)** means experience resulting from the perception of product or service appearance and color, form, materials, and texture are associated with this experience. For example, a respondent loved his Lamy safari because of the shape and texture of the fountain pen.
- **Amusement in interaction (SE2)** is about joy or satisfaction related to sensorial feedbacks that are directly or indirectly made between product or service and user. For instance, a respondent told he loved Palomino Blackwing pencil because it gave him good tactile feeling while writing or drawing.
- **Atmosphere or impression (SE3)** means secondary and consequential emotion aroused from identical or mixed sense(s) during using a product or service, and usually this mood or feeling represents characteristics of product or service itself. For instance, a respondent loved the Original Sound Track of his favorite musical because it aroused him joyful emotion.
- **Sensorial comfort (SE4)** is experienced when a user feels comfortable resulting from the interaction between product or service and user during usage without disrupted by unexpected stimuli. According to a story of a respondent she loved her bedclothes just because it delivered her deep comfort.

Instrumental Experience (see examples in Figure 5)

- **High functionality (IE1)** is experienced when a product or service performs better than the expectation of the user. The terms such as effectiveness, functional variety and usefulness belongs to this subcategory. A respondent was fond of Geforce Titan X, graphic card for PC because it incredibly enhanced graphical performance of his computer when he played a computer game.
- **High durability (IE2)** means how a product works well without failure, or how long the product lasts without any malfunction. For example, a respondent said he liked his gas boiler because it was hardly broken compared to what he had used before.

SE1 Lamy's Safari

SE2 Blackwing, a pencil

SE3 OST of a Musical

SE4 Bedclothes

Figure 4. Examples of sensory experience sub-categories.

- **Simplicity (IE3)** is about how easily users can achieve his/her goal during the usage of a product or a service. Ease to use such as functional simplification can explain this subcategory. For instance, a respondent mentioned that her Aeropress machine is easy to make brewed coffee and functionally simple.
- **Efficiency (IE4)** is about how well a product or a service works efficiently in terms of users' efforts, time or economical cost. It is distinguished from high functionality in a sense that functionality is about how well product or service achieves instrumental goals. Usually, efficiency is more related to the amount of a resource necessary to achieve one task compared to functionality. A respondent selected her coffee machine called Kitchen Art Plus because the machine helped her to save time in case of boiling water.

Episodic Experience (see examples in Figure 6)

- **Extrinsic meaning (EE1)** means an experience to be evoked by other people. The typical example is gift and a person has a positive user experience with a product or a service when it is given by somebody else to celebrate an event of or to

compensate for an achievement done by the receiver. For example, a middle-aged man participated in the survey told that he had got a necktie from his beloved daughter for the first time in his life. He loved the product just because it was presented by his daughter for the first time.

- **Intrinsic meaning (EE2)** refers satisfaction experienced because of product (or service)-related episode. This includes monumental experiences such as first-time experience, however it is still from a single accident in the past. While extrinsic meaning is delivered by others, intrinsic meaning is made by the user himself or herself. In the survey, a respondent mentioned his Daewoo car as his favorite product, which had been owned at the first time in his life.
- **Retrospective experience (EE3)** tells the cases resulting from a series of anamnestic experiences related to users' product or service, or the users' product or service experience during a particular period. For example, one respondent said he likes Yakima's speaker because it is quite old and makes crackling sound as like as radio used in his younger days.
- **Troubleshooter (EE4)** is based on experience aroused when products or services help users physically or psychologically solve problems which

IE1 Geforce's Titan

IE2 a Gas boiler

IE3 a Coffee brewer

IE4 a Coffee machine

Figure 5. Examples of instrumental experience sub-categories.

EE1 a Necktie

EE2 Daewoo, a car

EE3 Yakima's speaker

EE4 a Bidet

Figure 6. Examples of episodic experience sub-categories.

they had experienced. For instance, a respondent was able to resolve her defecation problem by using a bidet and the product became her favorite product in her daily life.

made up with organically cultivated materials standing for environmental sustainability. A respondent also mentioned Aoyama Flower Market flower scissors as her most favorite because the scissors stands for small relax between our busy daily lives.

Value Experience (see examples in Figure 7)

Symbolic Experience (see examples in Figure 8)

- **Self-improvement (VE1)** refers to positive user experience originating from personal or psychological growth such as improvement of ability, self-administration, self-realization, motivation or satisfying desires through the usage of product or service. According to the survey result, a candle warmer, for example, was mentioned as most favorite product because it helped her to keep improving herself mentally.
- **Personal value (VE2)** means experience made when a product or a service reflects personally pursued ideas or values well. Personal value represents personal preference through products or services. It includes uniqueness, early-adoption, communication, safety and so on. For instance, a male respondent selected a unique hip sack as his favorite because it was not a common style bag everyone carries.
- **Common benefit (VE3)** means personally accepted values commonly shared in the society, such as social norms, cultural value, or ideology. Common benefit is usually affected by interests of group or society that the person belongs to. Cosmetic product called Artistry was one of most favorite products in the survey. She loved it because it was

- **Social recognition (SyE1)** means that a product user wants the user or his/her society to be considered as having distinguished characteristics from others by using product(s) of specific brand. A respondent using a backpack, answered that she thought as if she became a person to have a good sense of design by carrying the bag.
- **Brand image/identity (SyE2)** refers to experience in relation to impression, aura, or symbolic image which a brand aims to deliver and it is something to be commonly recognized in a society. A female respondent said she liked Nike's running shoes because it represents young, energetic and urban health lifestyle.
- **Brand credibility (SyE3)** means experience resulting from trust and confidence that a brand implies while a user experiences the brand direct or indirectly. Multiple numbers of respondents said they support and trust Apple's iPhone because the brand Apple has strong brand credibility.
- **Sense of belonging (SyE4)** refers to experience made when a user feels homogeneity and solidarity by using the same kind of product or

VE1 a Candle warmer

VE2 GFLAT's hip sack

VE3 Artistry(cosmetics)

VE3 Flower scissors

Figure 7. Examples of value experience sub-categories.

Figure 8. Examples of symbolic experience sub-categories.

Figure 9. Positive user experience trend throughout product types.

service with others. A pair of Air Jordan shoes was mentioned as favorite product in the survey. The reason of liking the product was that they are all numbered and it provides the user with connection between people who wear the shoes.

Evaluation of each positive user experience attribute by product type

In all product types but home/decorations and stationaries instrumental experience had the highest

score among user experience attributes (Table 2). Sensory experience was secondly important attribute in those product types but this was not the case in some categories such as home appliances and service. Interestingly, respondents gave the highest score to sensory experience in case of home/decoration category. The other experiences did not show a particular pattern throughout product types (Figure 9). In case of episodic experience, it was most important in stationaries/hobbies category. The experience was

Table 2. Mean values of each user experience attribute according to product type.

Product type	N	Sensory Experience	Instrumental Experience	Episodic Experience	Value Experience	Symbolic Experience
Consumer electronics	28	4.00	4.50	2.79	2.96	3.50
Cosmetics/beauty	16	4.00	4.06	3.19	3.00	3.19
Sports	8	4.13	4.38	3.50	3.50	3.75
Computer accessories	8	3.38	4.75	2.88	3.13	2.75
Home appliances	7	3.57	4.14	3.57	3.71	3.14
Home/decorations	6	4.17	4.00	3.50	2.83	2.33
Stationaries	5	3.80	3.80	4.80	2.80	3.20
Service	17	3.00	4.47	2.76	3.47	2.59

least important in consumer electronics/electronic accessories and sports categories and almost least in cosmetics, computer-related products and service categories. Value experience was not highly scored throughout product types except for home appliances and service categories. Finally, symbolic experience also was not considered as an important attribute to explain why the respondents were fond of their product or service.

Most important attribute in positive user experience

Among 102 products and services, instrumental experience was most frequently mentioned as the most important positive user experience attribute. Sensory experience (19.6%) was secondly ranked, which was followed by symbolic (9.8%) and episodic (9.8%) experiences. value (2.94%) experience was least mentioned (Figure 10).

The usage stage and positive user experience attributes

Any products and services that the respondents mentioned as the most favorite one were not on the first stage of usage. From stage 2 to 5, there were 4, 21, 69, and 8 cases, and the scores of each attribute were averaged within the stage groups. User experience attributes showed patterns throughout the stage of usage (Figure 11). Instrumental experience had generally higher scores than the other throughout all the stages of usage. Sensory experience and value experience showed their lowest scores at stage 5. On the contrary, episodic experience could be considered as a main contributor at the stage, and it showed much higher score than any other stages' scores. In case of symbolic experience, it showed relatively higher score at 'First use' and 'Ongoing use: Phase 1' stages, but it had the lowest score at the stage of 'Discarding or Changing'.

Figure 10. Percentages of the most frequently mentioned attribute of positive user experience.

Discussion and conclusions

Product type and positive user experience

When the respondents were asked about their most favorite product or service, consumer electronics were most frequently mentioned. This might be explained by the phenomenon that consumer electronics have been featured by many novel functions such as music player, camera and fitness aid and at the same time they have been increasingly popular and pervasive to our everyday life. The secondly often mentioned product category was service and cosmetics. A possible explanation of why they became such lovely ones is that the quality of service has been increased as it is an important marketing strategy and people have been more and more exposed to the positive experience from such service. Escaping the period when functionality and performance are important, much attention to personal care has been paid until recently. This seems to lead to more and easier consumption of cosmetic products. Along with the interest, the quality of cosmetics has also been improved probably thanks to technological advance. It could explain why people often mentioned cosmetic

Figure 11. Trend of positive user experience attributes over the stage of product usage.

products as their favorite products. Interestingly, consumer electronics, cosmetics and service are what has been radically improved in terms of quality and diversity recently. This radical improvement in quality and diversity could explain why people love a product or a service. In other words, positive user experience in a product category seems to be made depending on how novel and diverse experiences can be provided with people.

Sub-categories of positive user experience attributes

Five attributes of positive user experience were made on the basis of existing theories and models on user experience. Their definitions were useful to figure out how positive user experience is composed of. However, categorizing a case into one of them was sometimes confusing because positive user experience is an outcome of the interaction between entities such as user, product and context. With clear descriptions of positive user experience, subcategories of positive user experience attributes, it would help design practitioners easily figure out what attribute exactly stands for, on one hand. It could provide them with affluent knowledge of what and how attributes of positive user experience should be taken into consideration.

Evaluation of each positive user experience attribute by product type

Although most of product categories have their highest score in instrumental experience sensory experience and episodic experience were most important in home decoration and stationary categories respectively. Products within the home decoration category include tableware, dishes, book shelves, bedclothes, etc. Because these products are relatively simple-functioned and aesthetic-focused in many cases, sensory experience would be more importantly considered than their functionality. Most of favorite products within stationary category were souvenir from himself/herself or gift from others. Obviously, episodic experience is of importance reminding them of a story or a memory. To products used in open places such as gym and outside home, symbolic experience was also an important attribute next to instrumental and sensory experiences. Value experience is somehow evident only in home appliances and service. Considering that home appliances is closely related to health and energy saving issues, it makes sense that the experience could be as important as instrumental experience. As a representative of services, SNS has been used by many people and stimulates communication between people. Through the service, people feel emotions lacking today such as friendship, respect and intimacy. This can explain why value experience is secondly ranked among five attributes.

Distribution of the most important positive user experience attribute

As the results indicate, both instrumental experience and sensory experience can explain approximately 80% of the reasons why people love a product or a service. Especially, instrumental experience takes more than half of the reasons and this implies the

experience is seriously taken into consideration as a key element throughout product development process. Especially about instrumental experience, the difference may be made by the consumers' memories about achievement. According to the study of Hoch (2002), Instrumental value or goal of consumers tends to be relevant and involving to the consumers, and Huffman and Houston (1993) found consumers' memory improved when the experience was organized around their goal. In other words, instrumental attributes could be easily perceived by the consumers than others.

The usage stage and positive user experience attributes

We found out that dominant attributes of positive user experience differ according to the stage of product usage. Even though the scores for each usage stage are not always based on the same types of product, it is meaningful to compare tendencies between usage stages in terms of UX. A product usage stage at which a certain attribute works relatively stronger than the others in positive user experience could be indirectly anticipated by comparing these tendencies. When people purchase or own a product or a service, its instrumental, sensory, value and symbolic attributes are already considered in the phase. Except for instrumental experience (hard to depreciate due to the ultimate goal to have it), the importance of those experiences tend to decrease over time because they are characterized as momentary experience which does not last long. As episodic experience is something to be accumulated during the usage period, it is the only experience to tend to increase over time. In many cases, people still own the product because of their episodic experience with the product or service although the product had been already out of use. This finding is in line with the study of Karapanos (2010). According to him, as time goes by familiarity (stimulation and learnability), functional dependency and emotional attachment are key attributes of product experience in order across the usage of the product.

The study redefined five attributes of positive user experience and empirically identified the validity of the taxonomy with our everyday products and services. In addition to that, it revealed how attributes of positive user experience are in relation to product types. Considering that most of studies in user experience have dealt with overall experience regardless of usage period, the finding that positive user experience is dependent upon time is meaningful. Nonetheless, the study has some limitations. The sample could make the results biased because half of the respondents was students. It could work as the other limitation that they were from South Korea considering cultural background influences positive user experience and favorite products or services. Therefore, the limitations should be carefully taken into account for a further study.

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GRAND.C, beyond the temporality of nodes. Digitally and physically connecting generations through product service system design, a case study

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Abstract This paper describes a case study of an early stage product service system (PSS) design. By means of a specific PSS design methodology, we were able to include insights from various domains and their underlying processes, in order to enhance value creation (beyond the product). The context of this case study was to preserve and enrich the connection between grandchildren and grandparents. Throughout the entire process, PSS design tools enable an iterative way of involving different stakeholders that broaden the exploration of recognisable emotions during a person's life and more specifically with regard to the above-mentioned node 'becoming a grandparent'. The result, GRAND.C, is an enrichment service that allows grandchildren to snoop in the past of their grandparents and is based on an authentic user experience, free play and verbal tradition. This is presented through a detailed system map and simplified customer journey, as well as a visual prototype and photo novel. It is confirmed that the prototype in particular is a very meaningful means to reinforce the design brief and to communicate the concept to the end user.

Keywords *Product service system design, Intergenerational relationships, Pleasurable experiences, Storytelling, Prototyping*

Introduction

Product Service System (PSS) design toolkit

Advancements in electronics, information and communication technology are introducing new elements to the design process and require a systematic rethinking of how designers integrate both tangible and intangible components. "PSS" can provide an opportunity to create innovative interactions between consumers, the products and services they use and the providers that offer these hybrids (Dewit & De Roeck, 2014). To support a product-service transition, the described PSS design toolkit is an ongoing collaboration (Design Flanders & Namahn, 2013; Dewit, De Roeck & Baelus, 2014; VVSG, 2013) and effort to develop a methodology, with tools and techniques (Figure 1), to design meaningful product-service systems. It includes valuable and up-to-date insights from a variety of domains and their underlying design processes: systems and systemic thinking, service design, human-centred design, interaction design, (user) experience design, product design and design thinking.

The design challenge

This research is based on the process and findings of a PSS design toolkit put to the test by 1st year master students in product development, in the context of 'nodes of life'. These landmarks of human life are

inspired by van Genep (1960), Elton and Reid (2010) and Vissers et al. (2012); e.g. leaving home, discovery and play, education, career, love, childbirth, investment, health, growing old and death.

Depending on the above-mentioned node(s), the design process runs through exploration, ideation, definition and verification, using a combination of tools specific for each phase. The goal of the project and its approach is not to seek the next large scale ecosystems, but aims to identify recognisable emotions during a person's life and to design whole product-service life cycles by means of a specific PSS design toolkit. The described project is more design-driven, with a focus on re-interpretation of meaning, rather than on performance or problem-solving (Verganti, 2009).

In this paper one specific case - GRAND.C - is highlighted in order to represent and visualise the process and usage of the PSS design toolkit, applied to the life-changing event of 'becoming a grandparent'.

Social and scientific relevance

The impact of becoming a grandparent in a lifetime is not to be underestimated. At a certain age you have to accept that your house gets invaded and you again have to take care of young children from time to time. However, an emotional bond with your grandchildren

Figure 1. Overview of the PSS tools (Design Flanders & Namahn, 2013).

is established in no time. Typically for this node is the **temporality**: “Looking back, time goes faster than you presume”.

To immerse in the theme of becoming a grandparent, an introductory literature review was undertaken in the field of **grandparent-grandchild relationships**. Partly due to demographic changes in Western societies, these relationships are posited to be more important, more intense and more prolonged than ever before, as stated in both popular and academic literature. (Bengtson, 2001; Fuller-Thomson & Minkler, 2001; Uhlenberg, 2009)

This strengthening mainly occurs during the childhood of the grandchild (Fuller-Thomson & Minkler, 2001; Uhlenberg, 2009). Noteworthy, the generation in between - the parents - can either facilitate or hinder the contact between grandparents and grandchildren. Thus, they play a key role as a lineage bridge or mediators (Kemp, 2005; Uhlenberg & Hammill, 1998). Kemp (2005) states that the importance of these mediators decreases when grandchildren grow older and more independent. Hence, as adults they keep in touch with their grandparents on their own terms.

Nevertheless before reaching adulthood, the rate of contact moments reduces when growing older (Silverstein & Long, 1998). That is why Cherlin and Furstenberg (1986) state that “the grandparent-grandchild relationship is considered to be the most intense before the grandchildren have reached adolescence”. To counteract this declination, Geurts and van Tilburg (2015) indicate that “a strong bond at an early stage of the relationship may hold back a decline in relationship intensity”. This idea of the link between the bond during childhood and adulthood is supported by three different studies (Brown, 2003; Geurts et al., 2014; Taylor et al., 2005).

Building on the premise of the bond between grandparents and grandchildren that needs to be prolonged, this case study aims to motivate grandchildren to keep in touch with their grandparents more intensively. Beyond a certain age

the visits to their grandparents are perceived rather boring and obligated. Thus, once the role of the parents as mediators declines, the intrinsic motivation of the grandchildren needs to be anticipated.

The PSS design framework (Figure 2) and toolkit (Dewit & De Roeck, 2014; Dewit, 2014) follows an affective or user (experience) point of view throughout its process, inspired on research by Gemser et al. (2012) and Ruitenberg and Desmet (2012). The framework visualizes what role the three front-end domains - exploration, idea generation and definition - play in the process of integrating and designing products and services in close relation to the user experience (Dewit, 2014).

Design process

Exploration

In the first phase of the design project we are looking for a clear value constellation. With various techniques an exploration is done on the activities, actors and experiences that play a role in different stages in the event of becoming a grandparent. These insights will be translated into a ‘design challenge’.

As mentioned in the literature review, the relationship between grandparents and grandchild is more important than ever before (Bengtson, 2001). Therefore the combination of grandparents and grandchildren as the most important stakeholders is chosen to proceed into the exploration phase.

Participative and user-centred techniques (e.g. in depth interviews) served as a qualitative and interrogative research methods for exploratory purpose, enabling constant involvement of the purposive sample of six grandparents (aged 58 - 80) and four grandchildren (aged 8 - 16) throughout the entire process.

A first tool, the **Stakeholders Experience Journey** tool (Figure 3), visualises a line of well being based on their experience being either a grandparent or a grandchild. Several key moments are chosen and marked with both positive and negative feelings. These milestones were

Figure 2. PSS design framework (Dewit, 2014).

Figure 3. Stakeholders Experience Journey.

important during the interview since the interviewers could ask some more profound questions on these topics to gain insights on this special bond.

It can be stated that there is a similar evolution in the bond between grandparents and grandchildren, as they grow older. This confirms the findings from the literature research. The following three stages are recognized each time: care stage, transition stage, and problem stage.

- *The care stage is characterized by an intensive contact during regular day care and thereby a deep and unconditional connection between grandparents and young grandchildren. Grandparents are a consistent safe haven with less rules and more fun. Additionally there is an extensive communication with the parents.*
- *In the transition stage the care providing function decreases and mostly the parents are responsible for visits of the grandchildren. The contact becomes rather superficial and less personal; after all the grandchildren are too young for a spontaneous visit.*
- *Finally the grandchildren are old enough to visit their grandparents independently, but they are so busy with their own life and unintentionally forget about their grandparents. This is what we call the problem stage.*

Beside these three stages we could recognise some recurring topics in the interviews; things that several grandparents or children indicated as remarkable in their experience.

“Grandparents are the grandchild’s link to the past. Grandchildren are a grandparent’s link to the future.” (G. de Keersmaecker, personal communication, October 21, 2013)

First of all, grandparents love nothing more than to talk about their past and family history. During the interviews grandparents intend to gather various additional objects while telling their stories and soon they even show the entire house. As Kornhaber and Woodward (1981) stated, grandparents can enact several roles, an important one is being the family historian. On the other hand, both female and male grandchildren are fascinated and look up to these stories. They as well chat about those typical things you can only find at your grandparents house.

Another topic was the fact that grandparents feel a little pushed aside when their grandchildren reach a certain age. As stated before, from the transition stage on, contact becomes less intense. Grandparents grow older what makes it more difficult to keep up with their grandchildren that live their modern lives. This generation gap makes that grandparents feel like they do not know much about their grandchildren’s’ personal lives. Of course they have pictures taken at family meetings or holidays, but most of the times this kind of information comes from the parents instead of the children themselves.

To conclude the exploration phase a **Design Challenge** is formulated: what is to be designed in the next

phase? In short it could be described as ‘**blending stories**’. The goal will be to avoid the problem stage by already anticipating during the transition stage. The product service will provide an opportunity for the grandchildren to communicate with their grandparents themselves, without the parents as a necessary intermediary. The outcome needs to be convenient and intuitive in use for both parties. It should be a means to exchange personal info in an unforced way, in order to strengthen the relationship during childhood. In this way, it can be avoided that the relationship intensity declines during adolescence and adulthood.

Ideation

In the ideation phase we are working towards a viable PSS idea. Therefore we defined design requirements, emotional and rational objectives that must be met. These serve as a starting point to gather inspiration and as evaluation criteria for the different PSS scenarios that will be considered.

In the **Lotus Blossom** technique (Figure 4) we combine the eight most important requirements with inspiring examples in different contexts in order to retrieve new characteristics and ideas by means of lateral thinking.

After completing this matrix, we realised that games and play are a powerful means to transform our goals into an actual design. A typical characteristic of every child, regardless of age or gender, is curiosity. Which child can say it has never been on a treasure hunt in their grandparents’ house before? The idea is born to trigger and facilitate this explorative behaviour in order to blend the grandparents’ stories from the past with the modern environment of today’s children.

A good example of a toy that allows children to explore their environment is Sniff (Figure 5). New technologies are used without children noticing. Instead of playing games on their parents’ iPad, Sniff uses the real world as game board and can therefore be classified as a pervasive game (Johansson, 2009). In this genre new kind of gameplay experiences are created by combining different contexts and using the real world as play area to aim for physical and social interaction (Montola, Stenros & Waern, 2009).

“It is not about making society more high-tech, instead it is about making technology more social.” (CUO Social Spaces, 2012)

As observed in the exploration phase, grandparents like to show old objects to enrich their stories. It makes it easier for children to fully understand the family history. But what if some of these objects are not available anymore? What if grandparents are living in a retirement home and had to leave most of their material belongings behind? What if grandparents want to show the fun of recording an audiotape, but their recording device has stopped working long before? These kinds of questions made us think about including a service to provide the grandparents access to authentic objects that they do not possess any more themselves.

Figure 4. Lotus Blossom.

Figure 5. Sniff (Johanson, 2009).

Figure 6. Visual representation basic system GRAND.C.

The best place to find these kinds of items is of course a thrift shop. Often these stores receive these valuable objects and sell them at a low price. But of course grandparents do not mean to buy old products again. This is how we came up with the idea of a rental service for old artefacts.

With our PSS concept we want to stimulate the long lasting connection between grandparent and grandchild. In a playful way we want to encourage the discovery urge of children on the one hand, and the preservation of cultural material heritage and family stories on the other hand.

Definition

In the definition phase we aim to translate the previous statement into clear product and service attributes. The project is concluded with a design brief to finalise all front-end activities and to give a head start for new product/service development that takes the PSS concept into implementation. Specifications and architecture for both the product and the service part in the system are described as far as needed. The design brief consists of a detailed system map, which

is also translated into a simplified, graphical representation of the customer journey, a visual prototype, a photo novel to communicate the PSS concept and interactions, and finally a first working prototype.

Our PSS concept is called GRAND.C (Figure 6); an enrichment service that consists of a Basic and Advanced system. It allows grandchildren to snoop in the past of their grandparents and it is based on an authentic user experience, free play and verbal tradition.

Figure 7 shows the complexity of the **detailed system map**, which was the basis for simplifying and refining the whole concept (the complete and readable diagram can be requested from the authors). It describes the proverbial journey, emotions and interactions of the users - grandparents and grandchildren - throughout the pre service, service and post service period. It highlights the touchpoints and channels of the GRAND.C product and service, with a focus on both tangible and intangible aspects.

Figure 7. Detailed system map.

Figure 8. Customer Journey of GRAND.C Basic product system.

Because of its complexity, the scheme is also visualised in a **simplified customer journey**. The **Basic product system** (Figure 8) contains a bird (reader), tags and a birdhouse. When one or more grandchildren come over for a visit, grandparents can prepare a quest. They hide the coloured tags together with old objects of value. Through visual feedback the birds help the grandchildren to locate the different tags (Figure 9). When a tag is found, grandchildren discover a meaningful artefact and can ask their grandparents for more information. Of course the grandparents love to tell some anecdotes. Therefore the artefacts serve as a trigger to support the personal stories of the grandparents. Via GRAND.C children explore their family history in a playful way. When going home, the grandparents can pass on small mementos (e.g. the recipe of grandmother's famous pudding), which they can collect in their personal birdhouse.

Figure 10 shows the representation of the service component of the system. In collaboration with thrift

shops, GRAND.C offers an **Advanced service system** with an extensive offer of old artefacts to enrich the grandparents' stories. From all products that are brought to thrift stores by customers, GRAND.C makes a selection of the most valuable items to enhance storytelling and manages the distribution to collaborating partners. Grandparents can lend specific objects via their online user account or they can wait for the GRAND.C bus that comes to the neighbourhood every now and then. When the grandchildren's quest is completed, the objects can be returned to the nearest thrift shop.

Verification

In the final phase we address the end user again in order to verify the PSS concept. Prototypes and a photo novel are used to introduce the concept and demonstrate the interactions.

In each PSS design process it is important to verify the concept with the end user. Therefore it is necessary to have a clear representation. For the GRAND.C project

Figure 9. Visual feedback to locate tags.

Figure 10. Customer Journey of GRAND.C Advanced service system.

we made a **visual prototype** of all the tangible components of the system. This makes it much more convenient to communicate with the end user. By introducing the PSS concept to the consumer, the prototype helps to demonstrate the interactions, which is way clearer than an abstract scheme.

Due to the prototype we were able to put this front-end concept into a realistic context. We contacted two grandchildren and their grandparents from the previous **user panel** and asked them to re-enact all aspects of the scenario (Figure 11). By letting them interact with the prototype in a way that approaches reality as close as possible, we could verify which elements of the PSS concept work well and which ones do not work as planned, before scaling up. The most important aspect to be tested is the value constellation: Do the children have fun during the game and is the game encouraging the grandparents to bring up personal stories that are fascinating the grandchildren?

The setting was the house of the grandparents, which is a familiar environment where the participants are at ease. The grandparents were asked to hide some tags with objects that they value. Because the prototype was not actually working, we helped the children to locate the tags by playing the classic hot and cold game combined with some other game mechanics. When a tag was found, the grandparents took some time to provide the children with several background stories.

In the next round some other game mechanics were included such as competing against each other, varieties in difficulty and other ways of searching, as these will also be present in the real GRAND.C game. In reality the different colours of tags will represent different levels with evolving kinds of visual feedback that will get harder to interpret.

This re-enacting of the scenario gave us the opportunity to capture every moment in the customer journey and make a detailed photo novel to communicate the total concept to the end user. By watching this novella, the user can easily empathize with the story, which makes it possible for us to gather feedback on all aspects of the product service system.

This verification method gave us confirmation of the capability of GRAND.C to turn a regular visit into a valuable moment of interaction between two generations. The game creates a pleasurable moment for the children but in the end it is just the medium to stimulate that special relationship between grandparents and grandchildren which they will value both significantly in the long term. Additionally, society will benefit from GRAND.C as well, since the preservation of an important aspect of cultural heritage is supported

In order to further evaluate the game mechanics, we made a second prototype of the bird (Figure 12), provided with real-time visual feedback to locate a tag. Here, we aimed to implement electronics without losing the aesthetic qualities of the first prototype. By using two Bluetooth modules, coded in Arduino, we were able to put the received signals in different ranges and make it possible to distinguish distances. This input is converted into visual feedback; the closer the bird approaches a tag, the more lights will go on.

With this prototype we could conduct another user test with less interference of the researchers. Figure 13 shows a participant using the bird to search a tag. Finally the prototype was showcased at 'Buzzkruit' Expo in Antwerp, where visitors could try out the game and react to the concept (Figure 14). On this link below a video can be found where the concept is explained (in Dutch) as well as a quick demonstration of the prototype: <https://vimeo.com/135117515>

Figure 11. Scenario re-enacting.

Figure 12. Electronic prototype.

Figure 13. User test with electronic prototype.

Figure 14. GRAND.C exposed at Buzzkruit.

The concept of GRAND.C can be assessed through the PSS strategy and typology. Tukker and Tischner (2006) distinguished eight different PSS categories, going from Product Oriented to Result Oriented (Figure 15). GRAND.C consists of two components with each a different focus. The Basic product system can be situated in the category of a **Product related service**. The bird readers, tags and bird houses are sold as a product, but are combined with a product related service. This Advanced service system of GRAND.C concerns the collecting and lending of valuable artefacts through the GRAND.C bus and thrift stores. Therefore it can be positioned in the category of **Product renting**, which is more Use Oriented.

Discussion and future research

The context of grandparents and grandchildren is one almost everyone can relate to. Nevertheless the product service system (PSS) tools, which combines a variety of existing perspectives (such as human-centred design), provided a structured framework to indulge in this node of life and gain new insights during the exploration and ideation phase, with a clear focus on the service aspect of PSS. Especially the

tools where interaction with the stakeholders was required, gave us the opportunity to get inspired by the personal anecdotes of our test users. Each one of their unique experiences triggered some out of the box thinking.

We noticed that the first PSS tools (during the exploration phase) are rather focused on 'words' such as the Design Challenge and Requirements. Yet, from these concepts we reached a turning point with the Lotus Blossom. The design process suddenly became more visual and tangible through the use of inspirational examples that could meet the requirements. It helped us to translate the needs and wishes to attributes and interactions.

More opportunities for the PSS design toolkit lie in adding useful and diverse techniques supporting the definition and verification phase. PSS design is situated in the front end of innovation and aims for a valid concept. Therefore the outcome should be verified with the end consumer and communicated in an understandable manner.

Figure 15. Position of GRAND.C Basic & Advanced in the categories of PPS (Tukker & Tischner, 2006).

At the start of this design assignment, ten users were involved throughout the design process, from introductory interviews to user testing. However, more participants - both grandparents and grandchildren - would be advisable to generalise the obtained information and feedback. Nevertheless it must be stated that even with this limited test group, similar information was gathered as designated by the preliminary literature research. In addition, this small group allowed us to elaborate on various aspects during the interviews and user testing, resulting in more qualitative information. Also, we could have utilized existing tools, such as Positive Emotional Granularity Cards (Yoon, Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013) and the Negative Emotion Typology (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2013) in order to improve the naming of positive and negative emotions during the interviews.

GRAND.C was carried out in the context of a student design assignment with a rather determined time schedule and guidance. However, in other situations more time could have been invested in different phases of the design process. For example, it would have been interesting to explore the context of co-creation, which gives the opportunity to really involve test users during every stage of the design process and bringing them all together to discuss the conclusions and concepts.

During the final phase we chose to develop a visual

and low-tech prototype and experienced this as a meaningful and grateful way to communicate a complex system to stakeholders of different age categories. In other words, the GRAND.C prototype proved to be highly valuable for initial verification of the PSS concept. It allowed us to observe the rich interactions between grandparents and grandchildren, between grandchildren, and between these users and the different components of GRAND.C. Therefore we recommend more tools related to prototyping and user testing, as they should lead to more verified product service systems.

Although a visual prototype and product-service concept were validated, it remains uncertain how users respond to the new product-service throughout its entire life cycle. The next step would be to iterate on the findings and to develop a fully functional prototype of both service (e.g. thrift store rental and application) and product (e.g. the game mechanics and interfaces) components in the system for more extensive user testing.

In addition, it would be interesting to conduct research on the long-term effects of using GRAND.C compared to a reference group of non-users. Will users visit their grandparents more often during adolescence? Will they feel a deeper connection through shared emotional experiences? Will they know more about their family history?

Conclusion

In this PSS design assignment we did not aim for solving big problems concerning grandparents and grandchildren. By using the PSS design toolkit we could focus on exploring the whole context and the emotions that occur during the event of becoming a grandparent. After a literature review and primary research we discovered that from a certain age, visits to the grandparents are reduced to occasional, rather dull events. Here, we saw an opportunity to anticipate this stage by creating a stronger connection between the two different generations before the children reach adolescence and are fully occupied with their own lives.

The outcome of the design process is GRAND.C, a PSS concept to stimulate a long lasting connection between grandparent and grandchild. The product system offers a game for children to go on a treasure hunt in their grandparents' house and explore their family history in a playful way. The service component allows grandparents to rent other valuable objects to extend the possibilities of telling interesting stories.

As this design case is situated in the front end of innovation, the design process did not result in a 'final' product, but in a detailed system map where all interactions and touchpoints are described. However it is important to define the whole system in order to proceed in the stage of New Product/Service Development, this kind of scheme is not useful to verify the concept with the end user.

By introducing the prototype to a user panel and re-enacting the prescribed scenario, we could verify the capability of GRAND.C to evoke stories and the willingness of grandchildren to hear these stories and explore their family history.

We succeeded in designing a product service system that fits into the PSS strategy. The specific case study of GRAND.C can be situated in the PSS model as a rather product focused concept. The tangible objects (bird and tags) have a significant role. As stated by Dewit and De Roeck (2014): "Without a dedicated product the PSS cannot exist. The product carries specific aesthetic qualities and allows embedding emotion, personal meaning in the product".

However, the service component allows the eco-system to be longer involved with the customer. The user experience does not end after playing the GRAND.C game, it can proceed much longer since the GRAND.C service constantly introduces new objects that evoke new stories every time. Thus combining both product and service components in one system results into a better user experience that lasts longer.

It can be stated that GRAND.C provides a pleasurable moment for both grandparents and grandchildren when the game is played. The game is a means to create a stronger connection on the long term that both parties will significantly benefit. Additionally GRAND.C supports the preservation of important cultural heritage. With all these ingredients, GRAND.C reconnects two generations digitally and physically in

order to look beyond the temporality of this special node of life.

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Questioning the choice overload effect through design research

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Abstract Choice overload is a negative effect caused by a great variety of options in the user's choice experience. Researches have shown that, with the increase in the number of options, pleasure and satisfaction were negatively affected. Our aim was to measure the impact of the diversity of alternatives in the beauty and hygiene segment over the user choice experience. In an experiment (n=96), the diverse quantity of choice was manipulated using different types of packaging, a characteristic element of design projects. Based on sales catalog's information from a major company in this segment, three experimental conditions were generated: the first had 50% of the average amount of products found on the catalogs; the second had the average number of options found for the products; the third encompassed 50% more from the mean options from the catalogs. Results indicated the opposite of other researches on choice overload: users had more positive experiences when facing the biggest quantity of options (50% above the average of the quantity found in the market). These results have implications to product portfolio planning and can be used as a base to provide pleasurable experiences to consumers.

Keywords *Choice overload, Choice experience, Amount of alternatives*

Introduction

In the contemporary world, designers tries to deal with technical aspects of projects, as well as its impact on user experiences. It is a common assumption in the modern society that the bigger the number of choices, the better. People are accustomed to have different options to choose from and many express a desire for having more options. That is not necessarily a good idea, as there are cognitive limits to how much information people can process about products and services when making decisions. Following this reasoning, the choosing task often is felt as suffering (Iyengar; Agrawal, 2010).

According to Iyengar and Agrawal (2010), psychological studies have consistently shown the difficulty of comparing and contrasting attributes of more than seven different elements. In addition, people tend to become overloaded and frustrated when confronted with cognitive requirements of choice. The authors state that, as a result, people may (1) abdicate to make a choice completely, (2) reach to a more familiar choice, or even (3) make a poor decision, leading to a lower satisfaction.

While people may often be attracted by the variety of options in the market, it has been suggested that this overabundance can lead to adverse consequences, such as: decreased motivation to make the choice, to commit to a choice, or to make any choice (Iyengar; Lepper, 2000); a decrease in the strength of preference and satisfaction with the chosen option (Chernev, 2003; Iyengar; Lepper, 2000), and an increase in negative emotions, including disappointment and

regret (Schwartz, 2004).

This phenomenon has been called "choice overload" (Iyengar; Lepper, 2000); the "problem of too much choice"; the "tyranny of choice" (Schwartz, 2004); or the "too-much-choice-effect" (Scheibehenne; Greifeneder; Todd, 2009). The consensus among these terms is the idea of the adverse consequences caused by the increased number of options to choose from, which can negatively impact the user choice experience. Commonly viewed as a marketing thread, handling choice overload becomes a design problem as the area seeks development on understanding all the factors involved in managing design and, hence, the management of the product portfolio diversity.

Therefore, this study intends to understand the aspects which influence the occurrence of choice overload. Using a basic design element, the packaging and its shape, which was chosen for the easy manipulation by isolating one variable without being affected by others. This research aims to collaborate to avoid choice overload, in order to promote a positive choice experience for users facing a diversity of options. In this study, a positive choice experience is defined as the one where the user feels pleasure, manage to choose without difficulty, is less frustrated and more satisfied with the choice experience (Iyengar & Lepper, 2000; Shah & Wolford, 2007; Kobayashi et al., 2011).

Choice overload

Researchers on the phenomenon of choice overload, according to Scheibehenne, Greifeneder and Todd

(2010), argue that the negative effects do not always occur, but depend on certain prerequisites. An important precondition is the lack of familiarity or previous preference among the options so that the choice maker do not choose only something that matches their own preferences (Iyengar; Lepper, 2000). Chernev (2003) showed that people with clear previous preferences prefer to choose from larger assortments. For these people, the probability of choice and satisfaction increased with the number of options to choose from, the opposite of choice overload. For this reason, experiments with choice overload use unfamiliar options to whom will make the choice, thus avoiding strong previous preference for a particular option and, consequently, a highly selective search process that allow participants to ignore most part of the assortment (Scheibehenne; Greifeneder; Todd, 2009).

According to Shah and Wolford (2007), most research in this topic compared only two size groups, with number options with an average of 6 units (small group) and 24 (major group). Although the number of choice options is the core hypothesis on choice overload, there is no exact definition of what constitutes a lot of options.

A variable to consider is the perceived variety of the assortment, since the perception of variety can be equal to the real variety or not (Kahn, 1998). The author believes that large assortments can be negatively perceived by consumers if, instead of offering choice possibilities, they seem monumental and frustrating. As an example, the author mentions a Chinese restaurant menu on which the selection usually involves four types of meat (chicken, shrimp, beef and pork) and different sauces. Every possible type of combination is listed separately, making the perceived range to be large, while the actual assortment would be better understood if it was described in only two attributes. Thus, the author believes that when the array is processed in a simple and enjoyable way or when the consumer is motivated, the perception of a lot of variety is better than a little variety. However, when the processing is difficult, little variety might be preferred.

There are two factors which contribute to the perceived variety, according to Kahn (1998): the number of acceptable choices and the desired amount of diversity among the items. For the author, the sheer number of options is a type of diversity. For example, an ice cream parlor offering 31 flavors appears to offer more flexibility and range than the one that offers two or three options, regardless of which flavors. According to the author, if the user sees little or no difference between items of a product class, then the perception of abundance will also be low. Thus, the amount of diversity that consumers desire in an assortment is a function of the acceptability of the items and the distinction among these.

For Scheibehenne, Greineder and Todd (2010), on a theoretical perspective, the choice overload hypothesis defies most models of choice in psychology and economics, which believe that the increase of a set of

options does not leave the decision maker in a worse situation. In a practical perspective, a decrease on satisfaction or motivation due to the diversity of choice would require companies to rethink their practices of providing more and more kinds of products because they could increase their success if they had less to offer.

To Iyengar and Agrawal (2010) most companies do not reduce the number of products they offer because they are afraid of losing shelf space to competitors. However, the authors suggest that a careful cut can reduce costs, increase sales and improve the experience of choice for consumers. Kahn (1998) believes that, often, large assortments contain many redundant or duplicate options, which makes the choice more difficult. According to the author, to reduce users' confusion and maintain a sense of variety, extinguishing redundant items is enough.

In the mid-1990s, when Procter & Gamble (multinational of the health and beauty segment) decreased the range of the anti-dandruff shampoo Head & Shoulders, from 26 to 15, by eliminating less popular ones: sales increased by 10% (Goldstein, 2001 apud Shah; Wolford, 2007). This strategy, according to Kahn (1998), increased profitability and, in some categories, consumers perceived the assortment better with 35% less amount of units.

Thus, Iyengar and Agrawal (2010) propose that, if the market for a product is saturated with a variety of options, one should not seek a competitive advantage by providing more choices on the shelves. Instead, the authors suggest turning the selection process in a more positive and easier experience for consumers.

Hypothesis

As a stimulus to support this research, we selected the hygiene and beauty sector. According to the Brazilian Association of the Cosmetic, Toiletry and Perfumery Industry (ABIHPEC), Brazil is the third largest consumer in the world of cosmetics. Hygiene and beauty products are distributed in Brazil mainly in three ways: direct sales, network of franchised stores and traditional channels (supermarkets and pharmacies, etc.).

Based on this data, it was developed and experiment in order to measure the choice overload effect. The premise of this study, and of studies on choice overload (Iyengar and Lepper, 2000; Shah and Wolford, 2007; Kobayashi, Miki, Hiroyasu et al, 2011) is that, while providing many choices initially seem attractive to the participant, it can impair various aspects of the quality of choice experience. We then formulated the following hypothesis:

H₁: with the reduced number of choice alternatives, the user has more pleasure in the experience;

H₂: with fewer options, the user has less difficulty on making the choice;

H₃: with fewer options, the user feels less frustration with the choice experience;

H₄: with limited number of choice alternatives, the user has greater satisfaction in the experience.

On the perception of the amount of options to choose from, the hypothesis is that:

H₅: the user perceives he/she has many choices (too many alternatives) when finding a set with greater diversity of options than usually found in the market.

Scheibehenne et al. (2009) proposed that users with well-defined preferences before making the choice prefer more choice alternatives, as they have more chance of having their own to match. The authors suggest that the lack of clear goals and preferences before a decision can moderate the effect of choice overload, as individuals with well-defined preferences are more willing to make a choice and be satisfied with the alternative chosen among many options, since their preference can be matched. In addition, the likelihood of these preferences are met increases with the number of options available, leading to the opposite effect to the decision makers, where more is better. Therefore:

H₆: users with prior preferences among the evaluated products enjoy large amounts of alternatives.

The hypothesis will be tested using the data obtained in the experiment described below.

Methods

The experiment examined the effect of the number of options (independent variable) - manipulated through the diversity of shapes of hygiene and beauty products packaging – on pleasure, difficulty, frustration, satisfaction and perception of quantity, on the consumer's choice experience (dependent variables). The packages were chosen as a visual stimulation, as they allow easy manipulation of the shape variable without other interferences such as color, brand and texture.

The quantities of options used in the experiment were important for the research design. As identified through the analysis of empirical studies described in the introduction, it is not clear how the amount used in other experiments has been set. In their studies, Iyengar and Lepper (2000, p. 996) defined a limited amount of choice in about six units "as presented in previous experiments", and the extensive choice condition with number of options "reasonably large, but not ecologically unusual". Thus, it was detected the need to establish a parameter to relate what is a small, a medium or a large amount of packaging.

In this study, the amount of choice in the catalogs was defined from a mean of shampoo, conditioner and liquid soap options present in the Natura brand catalogs. This company is appointed as leader on the direct selling market in Brazil (COMESTICOSBR, 2010), distributing 24 books/magazines in cycles throughout the year. These catalogs are printed or can be accessed through the company website.

For the sample, it was used magazines from the cycles 11/2011 to 9/2012 (totaling 15 cycles), present in the Natura website in the period of 8th to 15th of May, 2012. This time frame was set to stipulate a universe of which the data would be acquired, ensuring the neutrality of the research. The magazines of this period were fully examined in order to count the amount of packaging of shampoo, conditioner and liquid soap presented. For the counting of products, two criteria were determined: it was only considered products which contained the words "shampoo", "conditioner" and "liquid soap" in their name; refill packs composing a set were not counted. This resulted in the averages: 21.47 (SD = 1.37) shampoos, 20.24 (SD = 1.64) conditioners and 14.71 (SD = 2.37) liquid soaps.

To manipulate the variables in the experiment, it was determined an average of the total number of shampoo, conditioner and liquid soap containers presented in the catalogs. From this average three groups were defined, two experimental groups (EG) and one control group (CG): (1) 50% of the average amount of options (reduced condition, experimental group 1 - EG1), (2) the average amount of options detected in the evaluated catalogs (market average, control group – CG) and (3) 150% of the average amount in the catalogs (expanded condition, experimental group 2 - EG2), as can be seen in Table 1. Therefore, the variable 'amount of alternatives' was manipulated in three levels.

The means were rounded to simplify the calculation and provide integers for the amount of packaging used in the catalog simulation on the experiment.

Instrument and procedures for data collection

The data collection procedure was carried out at universities computer rooms. Teachers were contacted, with authorization from the universities administration, and the students were taken to the laboratory, together with the researchers.

Three catalogs were produced in Adobe Indesign software for different manipulation conditions (reduced condition (EG1), market average (CG) and expanded condition, EG2). For the catalogs, it was selected images from an image bank from the internet,

Table 1. Average of packages per group.

Group	Shampoo	Conditioner	Liquid soap
50% (EG1: reduced condition)	11 (10,5)	10	7
100% (CG: market average)	21	20	14
150% (EG2: expanded condition)	32 (31,5)	30	21

Source: The authors.

and these were treated in Adobe Photoshop to have the same color (Figure 1).

In the rapport participants were asked to imagine they needed to buy the products - shampoo, conditioner, liquid soap - to their homes and they should choose one of each product from the catalog. Also, the questionnaire was answered individually. The data collection took in average 20 minutes and was conducted between August and October of 2012 in higher education institutions in Southern Brazil.

The catalog was available on a website to be accessed by the participants. On the website, the instructions for the participant were to initially browse the catalogue until the end and then complete the questionnaire. Everyone who accessed the website saw only one of the three catalogs. Participants did not know about the differences of catalogs, and the experimenter did not know which catalog the participants would see, since the process was totally random.

After reading the instructions and browse the entire catalog, participants filled out a questionnaire divided into: record of the choices and participant information, experience of choice evaluation, and perception about the number of options to choose from. In the first part, participants recorded their choices, indicating the page on which the product was found, allowing the simulation of a real choice made with the catalog. Also, participants completed questions about gender, age and occupation. The second stage of the questionnaire was based on Iyengar and Lepper (2000), in order to evaluate the user choice experience. Responses were supplied through a Likert scale from one (1 - not at all) to seven (7 - extremely). Thus, the questionnaire sought to examine how the choice experience was pleasurable ("How much did you enjoy making the choice?"), difficult ("Did you find it difficult to make the choice?"), satisfactory ("How happy did you feel making the choice?") and frustrating ("How frustrated you felt when you made the choice?").

Besides the choice experience, in the third stage, the questionnaire included questions to assess the users' perceptions about the number of options provided. It was asked participants if they thought they had the right number of options for shampoo, conditioner and liquid soap packaging, in order to make the choice. ("Do you think you had the right number of shampoo options in order to make the choice?"; "Do you think you had the right number of conditioner options in order to make the choice?"; "Do you think you had the right number of liquid soap options in order to make the choice?"). The answers were given on a Likert scale of seven points, anchored in three points: one (1) equivalent to "I felt I had very few options to make the choice, four (4) "I had the right number of options to make the choice" and seven (7) to "No, I had too many options to make the choice".

Another question served to assess whether the participant's preferences influenced the response, according to the prior preference hypothesis

Figure 1. Catalogue example for the reduced condition (EG1).

(Scheibehenne et al., 2009). This item was evaluated by the question "If you buy any of these products, how much would you say the choices you normally do influenced the choices in this research?". Answers ranged from "extremely influenced", "influenced a lot", "moderately influenced", "somewhat influenced" to "not influenced at all".

At this stage, a final question was added to ensure the users have flipped through the entire catalog before answering the questionnaire: "Have you looked at all the products before making the choice?" with the answers "yes" or "no". The respondents that chose "no" were excluded from the research.

Sample and sampling

Ninety-six (96) undergraduate students participated on the experiment (47.9% were female and 52.1% male), of which 32 were exposed to the reduced condition (EG1), 31 to the market average (CG) and 31 to the expanded condition (EG2).

Instruments and procedures for data analysis

Responses were electronically recorded through spreadsheets in Google Docs and converted to SPSS format. Descriptive statistics were held regarding the identification variables (gender, age) and Analysis of Variance (ANOVAS) between the answers given to questions relating to the dependent variables by the three different groups. Post-hoc enabled the comparison among the three groups. Pearson correlations were made between the perception of having the right number of options to make the choice and the prior preference for a product variable.

Results

The results obtained by manipulating the amount of product choices can be seen in Table 2.

No significant differences were detected between the means of agreement on issues about pleasure with the choice ($F(2, 93) = 0.144, p > 0.05$); difficulty ($F(2, 93) = 1.258, p > 0.05$); satisfaction ($F(2, 93) = 0.599, p > 0.05$); and frustration ($F(2, 93) = 0.475, p > 0.05$).

It was detected, on the question about the perception of having the right number of shampoo options in order to make a choice, that there is an effect on the

amount of alternatives on the assessment of having the right number of options to make the choice ($F(2, 93) = 5.41, p < 0.05$). Comparative analyzes between groups (Post Hoc) showed that the mean agreement of the expanded condition group (EG2), in relation to having the right number of options to choose from, can be considered greater than the reduced condition group (EG1) ($p < 0.05$) Cohen's effect suggests a large ($d=0.83$) significance. Furthermore, the mean agreement of the expanded condition group (EG2) can be considered greater than the mean of the control group (CG) ($p < 0.10$). Cohen's effect size value suggests a small to medium significance ($d=0,28$).

On the question about the perception of having the right number of choices of conditioner to choose from, it was detected the effect of the number of alternatives on the assessment of having the right number of options ($F(2, 93) = 5.93, p < 0.05$). In the comparative analysis between the groups (Post Hoc), the average agreement level of the expanded condition group (EG2) ($p < 0.05$), compared to having the right number of options to choose from, can be considered higher than the mean of the reduced condition group (EG1). For this comparison, Cohens effect size value is high

($d=0,76$). Also, the mean agreement of expanded condition group (EG2) can be considered greater than the mean of the control group (CG) ($p < 0.05$), with a small ($d=0,06$) Cohen's effect size significance.

About the number of liquid soap options, it was also detected the effect of the amount of alternatives on the evaluation of having the right number of options to select from ($F(2, 93) = 8.38, p < 0.001$). Comparative analyzes between groups (Post Hoc) showed that the average agreement of the expanded condition group (EG2) ($p < 0.05$), compared to having the right number of options to choose from, can be considered greater than the mean of the reduced condition group (EG1). Cohen's effect suggests a large ($d=0,98$) significance. Also, the mean agreement level of the control group (CG) can be considered greater than the mean of the reduced condition group (EG1) ($p < 0.05$) – with a high ($d=0,82$) Cohen's effect significance – and less than the mean of the expanded condition group (EG2) ($p < 0.05$), which shows a small ($d=0,19$) Cohen's effect value.

Despite detecting several significant effects, the choice overload effect was not found, since the diversity of alternatives did not generate adverse consequences to

Table 2. Experiment's descriptive results.

Questions	Experimental group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
How much did you enjoy making the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	4,31	1,60
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	4,27	1,31
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	4,13	1,36
	Total	96	4,24	1,41
Did you find it difficult making the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	3,44	2,00
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	3,33	1,81
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	4,06	2,13
	Total	96	3,60	1,99
How satisfied were you about making the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	4,91	1,77
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	4,48	1,62
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	4,61	1,33
	Total	96	4,67	1,58
How frustrated were you about making the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	2,41	1,62
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	2,58	1,90
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	2,84	1,77
	Total	96	2,60	1,76
Did you feel you had the right number of shampoo options to make the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	4,22	1,58
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	5,09	1,70
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	5,55	1,61
	Total	96	4,95	1,71
Did you feel you had the right number of conditioner options to make the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	4,13	1,48
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	5,22	1,54
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	5,32	1,64
	Total	96	4,90	1,63
Did you feel you had the right number of liquid soap options to make the choice?	50% (EG1: reduced condition)	32	3,56	1,56
	100% (CG: Market mean)	33	4,91	1,74
	150% (EG2: expanded condition)	31	5,26	1,91
	Total	96	4,57	1,87

Source: The authors.

the choice experience. The opposite has been identified: users perceive to have the right number of options to choose among different forms of shampoo, conditioner and liquid soap.

Furthermore, it was executed a Pearson correlation analysis between the issues related to the perception of having the right number of options to choose from (one for each product) and the perception of having suffered influence of previous preferences about the choices made (also assessed using specific questions for each product evaluated). The analysis considered the sample divided by groups (control group and experimental groups), which showed only a correlation (negative) significant referred to the choice of the conditioner in the control condition ($r = -0.464$, $p < 0.01$). Thus, it was not observed consistent correlations between the variables prior preferences in the segment and the perception of suitability of product mix increased, so that they do not relate.

Discussion and conclusion

The number of options to choose in the experiments were set from the average of the total number of packaging of shampoo, conditioner and liquid soap found in the Natura catalogs (cycles from 11/2011 to 9/2012). This time frame was set to determine an universe where the data would be acquired and guarantee the neutrality of the research. It also differentiates this research from others reviewed (Iyengar, Lepper, 2000; Scheibehenne, Greifeneder, Todd, 2009; Kobayashi, Miki, Hiroyasu et al, 2011; Shah, Wolford, 2007), because it was established a parameter to decide the amount of alternatives. From the average amount of the total number of packaging found, three groups were established: the market average condition (100%), other with the reduced number (50%) and a third condition with an expanded number of options (150%). Thus, it was possible to establish what is a small, a medium or a large amount of packaging, in relation to the market average.

The variables analyzed in the experiment, based on Iyengar and Lepper (2000), involved pleasure, difficulty of choosing, frustration, satisfaction and perception of right number of options in relation to the choice experience. The hypothesis H_1 to H_5 were denied: the results show that users perceive as more appropriate the set with expanded options.

Choice overload, pointed out by different authors (Iyengar, Lepper, 2000; Schwartz, 2000; Scheibehenne, Greifeneder, Todd, 2009) as an effect that causes adverse issues to the choice experience across diversity of alternatives, was not found in this study. Thus, it is noteworthy to designers that one can work with extensive product lines and still provide positive experiences to the user. Choosing through catalogs, according to the experiment results, appears distinct from other forms of decision discussed in the introduction of this paper. Portfolio management of the product in the segment deserves to be designed differently: more can be better.

This result is in favor of the arguments mentioned by Scheibehenne, Greifeneder and Todd (2009), who

question the hypothesis of choice overload. According to the authors, large assortments may have advantages, including: a wide variety of choices increases the probability of satisfying different individuals and thus serves to individuality and plurality; a wide variety available in one location reduces the cost of looking for more options; allow for direct comparisons among options, making it easy to have a global idea of the distribution quality. All these factors lead to a better informed and more confident choice. Hence, future studies on choice overload could consider the variety moderator in the beauty and hygiene segment.

A significant correlation between the perception of having the right number of options to choose from, and the previous preference variable was found on one (conditioner) of the three products used. The result contradicts what Scheibehenne, Greifeneder and Todd (2009) stated about the possible too-much-choice effect moderator. According to the authors, as the number of options increases, the more likely a consumer with well-defined preferences will find what pleases him/herself among the options. Therefore, the H_6 hypothesis, which proposed that users with prior preference appreciate lots of alternatives, was denied. This does not mean that they appreciate or not large sets of products to make the choice, but it means that the variables preference and suitability assessment of the set of alternatives were not related consistently in the study.

Also, the number of attributes to be evaluated by the consumer when making a choice may be taken into consideration. In this research, simple elements were employed: the shape of hygiene and beauty products. That's possibly the reason why participants preferred the expanded number of options, because there were not many attributes, besides the shape, to evaluate in order to make the choice. In the experiments analyzed, except for Kobayashi, Miki, Hiroyasu et al. (2011), the chosen products had more than one attribute, such as the pens used by Shah and Wolford (2007) or the list of restaurants and charities offered by Scheibehenne, Greifeneder and Todd (2010). Therefore, future studies could consider a wider range of attributes in the investigated segment.

Scheibehenne, Greifeneder and Todd (2010) point out the choice environment issue, about how researches on choice overload commonly refer to satisfaction with the chosen option, instead of the choice experience as a whole. In this research, the choice experience was evaluated in an artificial environment. Therefore, the research context may have caused the non detection of choice overload, since the decision did not offer consequences of a real choice, in the long term. Another future research opportunity is indicated by pursuing studies in more natural settings.

The experiment results show how important the perception of the number of options by the user is. Kahn (1998) believes that this variable must be considered when working with large amounts of products – preferred by the participants on this research - for the consumer to positively experience

the choice possibilities. The author indicates that it is important to know the user preferences, present a number that present flexibility of options, and items distinct from each other.

Therefore, by providing an extensive product portfolio in the hygiene and beauty sector, it is important to consider the perceived range variable, indicated by Kahn (1998). According to the author, the range should contain different items, so that the consumer perceives a varied and flexible assortment. Otherwise, with very similar items to each other, the user can negatively perceive the amount of items, causing frustration when making a choice.

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Human-centred design as part of measuring automotive perceived quality – Extending the product impact model

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Abstract Perceived Quality (PQ) is the current battle-ground for automotive manufacturers. It is accepted that most vehicles today are of an appropriate inherent and measureable *product quality*, so the current competitive edge is sought in tangible, demonstrable *Perceived Quality*.

PQ is directly related to Design and Emotion; the latter is a component in understanding why customers make purchases. Current, mostly commercial measures do not take into account all aspects of a purchase decision based on PQ. This paper looks at a wealth of previous research on PQ and proposes a new framework, building upon recent research looking at product impact, centred upon humans, developed by Delft University.

The perception of quality is personal and potentially very different for each consumer, so this paper sets out to understand how PQ is currently measured in the industry, as what is measured can surely be controlled, so manufacturers should welcome an improvement upon current measures of PQ.

The Product Impact Model makes it possible to access a real-time view of PQ from customers at points of sale, automotive shows, etc. Data gathered via this method will contribute to a better understanding of PQ, including how to measure and control it.

Keywords *Perceived quality, Emotive design, Measurement, Human factors*

Introduction

PQ is arguably a key component of the purchasing process. This paper sets out to define and measure PQ and is intended to follow a series of Design and Emotion (D&E) papers, which culminated in the Model of Product Impact (Figure 2). In order to make clear the difference between Product and Perceived Quality (PQ), these will be defined first, after an overview of product quality Standards. The paper will consider zones of automotive PQ (Figure 1), some currently available commercial measures and will move on to a literature review of PQ and D&E. The paper re-visits the Impact Model and then integrates it with the results of the literature review into a new model of PQ.

This paper aims to consider:

- *What current Literature provides quantitative and qualitative PQ measures,*
- *What are the current methods of PQ measurement in the Automotive Industry*
- *Can a model of product impact centred upon humans, be developed to give greater definition of customer PQ?*

In order to understand PQ better, it is useful to consider *product* quality and some well-accepted definitions follow, but first a look at standards. Today,

quality products are expected from any manufacturer or supplier. Sophisticated sets of objective measures have been developed to assess a product's quality.

Some are manufacturer or supplier-driven, others promoted by magazines or consumer organisations, yet more by national or international standards, for example:

- *Manufacturers – e.g. the BMW QZ (Qualitätszahl or Quality number) system. This is used by in-house Auditors to score a car for demerits, so the lower a score, the better the car is. Many manufacturers use something similar.*
- *Magazines and web-sites – many use a simple five star system, where five is best. This is familiar to those who recognise the star system rating for hotels.*
- *Consumer organisations – Which? uses a series of coloured symbols for instant consumer assessment, such as 'Best Buy', 'Don't Buy' 'Great Value' and 'Worth a look'.*
- *National Standards – in Europe and the UK, many old British Standards have been subsumed into EU ones - EN or Europäische Norm.*
- *The Stiftung Waherntest is a German standard for consumer protection, of which 96% of the population are aware. (Hamann, 2009)*

- *Japan has their own national version, Japanese Industrial Standard, or JIS.*
- *International Standards – the best known is the ISO (International Standards Organisation) and ISO 9001 is the current quality standard for a management system and is often used as a badge to show a company is offering quality products or services.*

The above measures or standards are not strong on cognisance of any human issues. This paper seeks to rectify that oversight.

Product Quality Definitions

Before considering Perceived Quality, there are many different definitions of Product Quality. These mainly centre on specifications and definitive metrics.

- *Does the product meet its specification?*
- *Is it to the correct dimensions?*
- *Is it the right colour?*
- *Are the material properties correct?*
- *Does it perform to design expectations?*
- *Does it meet a Standard?*

A thought-provoking alternative definition from the early days of the Japanese rise in manufacturing excellence (Taguchi, 1986) is, “what is the loss to society once the product is shipped?”

In his seminal work ‘Eight Dimensions of Quality’, David Garvin (Garvin, 1984) ranked issues that he considered defined product quality. These were:

1. Performance
2. Features
3. Reliability
4. Conformance
5. Durability
6. Serviceability
7. Aesthetics
8. Perceived Quality (PQ)

It is interesting that he should place Aesthetics at number 7, when how a product looks is arguably the first impression a potential customer might take. Features, in second place, are also aspects that a consumer can assess early on from brochures or on-line resources. Performance can really only be gauged from product use or experience, so would appear later in most assessments. It could be argued that Durability and Reliability are sub-sets of Performance. Nonetheless, this framework is a seminal piece of work on Quality definition, which does feature recognition of a place for PQ, albeit again with no real human-centred content.

In Garvin’s (1984) definition of PQ, he suggests that customers are not necessarily in possession of all the relevant facts about a product’s characteristics or features, yet have made a hire, loan or purchase intent decision. This is demonstrably true when the product in question is a complex device such as a vehicle, mobile telephone or computer.

Very few customers will be familiar with all the attributes of these products as they are so complex.

Consider your last purchase experience of one of these types of product – were you completely *au fait* with the product, or did a later discovery of unexpected attributes cause delight? Did the product have a ‘Wow moment’? (Gallo, 2012). Conversely, did a lack of expected feature cause irritation? Here is some recognition of the human-centred measures and issues.

Good feature is for example a trademark of Apple products. In “The Apple Experience”, Carmine Gallo (2012) explains that at Apple, Steve Jobs was inspired by the hotel chain Four Seasons and the following innovations, which when they appeared in the early 70’s made an impression on a young Mr Jobs:

1. Individual shampoo bottles
2. Fitness rooms
3. Comfortable, quality beds
4. Spas

Jobs did not invent ‘Wow factors’, but developed sound ideas he could relate to from a hotel chain. He was starting to see design from a human viewpoint. Innovation and good feature is often what the customer seeks in an automotive purchase (Sepahvand & Sanainasab, 2013). Fiat CEO Sergio Marchionne declared in July 2007 - “I want Fiat to become the Apple of automobiles. And the 500 will be our iPod” (Barry, 2007). So many companies relate back to Apple in their expressions of innovation and good design, itself a key component of PQ. While product Quality is more a science or issue of metrology, Perceived Quality strays into the realms of psychology (Bucknall, 2015).

Automotive Perceived Quality – what is it and how is it to be measured?

From the preceding definition of Product Quality, Perceived Quality is linked to innovation, good design, desirable features and principally how it makes the consumer feel. It has been variously described as being “like an attitude” (Ophius & Van Trijp, 1995) but also as a piece of engineering learning from the marketing discipline (Golder, Mitra, & Moorman, 2012).

As Matt Wilkinson (2013) comments in his book, “A bias towards rationalism and quantitative analysis cannot substitute an empathic feel for what will delight the customer”. So PQ may also be seen as being related to the field of customer empathy and Empathic Design to generate emotion.

Perceived Quality is more aligned to how the customer feels when selecting, purchasing and finally using and/or owning the product; the affective emotion of product experiences. As an example, consider the excitement and anticipation of the launch of any Apple-branded product. Once purchased, the Apple experience continues when the product is in the user’s own environment - there are videos on the Internet just praising the packaging.

For Automotive PQ, there are many elements, which are traditionally broken down into three main areas of the vehicle, the power unit bay, the cabin or passenger space and the luggage volume. This applies to all

Figure 1. Some examples of the vehicle zones and automotive PQ elements.

vehicles, even those not of a traditional “three-box” design layout. The principal elements are shown (Figure 1).

Current commercial PQ measures

Having looked at the definitions and standards for generic product quality and then defined PQ, some of the best-known commercially available PQ measurement systems will be shown. The aim is to show that these methods are not showing the whole story of PQ.

There already exist a number of measures of PQ in the commercial world and some are listed (Table 1). It is important to point out that being commercial measures, these are marketed and sold as a revenue-generation process. One of the best-known, the J D Power rankings, have developed over time and have even transformed into a consultancy service that provide in-house expertise to manufacturers. Each market has its own version of these tools, or merely uses the commercial offering as it can be found in its native North American.

The magazines tend to just give simple star ratings and aside from journalistic sensational headlines, provide little in the form of measureable or even comparable emotive statements about cars surveyed.

The automotive magazine-based rankings shown (Table 1) are specific to each market, although some publications and their televisual forebears (such as the BBC’s *Top Gear* brand) are cloned to suit local tastes and cultures (Porter, 2004).

ALG (a Truecar Company) each year surveys 30,000 recent car buyers asking for their ratings of brand quality. Through calculation, the index creates a brand score, which represents the recent consumer purchase.

Using a 100-point scale derived from survey respondents’ qualitative scores, an assessment of automotive brands is conducted. ALG do mention the subject of Emotion in their press articles, but their services “provide OEMs (Original Equipment Manufacturers) with early product feedback and findings that support optimal product launch, packaging and pricing strategies.” (ALG, 2012) This company has supplied consulting services to manufacturers for over 50 years and provides a well-respected residual value service for North American market cars, yet emotion and design is difficult to extract from their output. ‘Data, Analytics and Insight’ are three declared pivotal legs of their services, most of which concentrate on financial, marketing or buying trends.

The J. D. Power Surveys provided by McGraw-Hill Financial are however, the most widely used by the automotive industry.

Methodology

Having seen in the previous section that there are commercially available measures of PQ, the following will give a short review of available PQ up to the current date in 2016. In order to organise the reading, some clear topic areas became apparent and are discussed below.

A review was undertaken of currently available research into Perceived Quality and shows that from over 150 articles, papers and books, 80+ were worth critiquing to provide thesis material. As more was reviewed, an assignment of papers has been made, based upon:

- *Current PQ literature, found in only 5 articles or papers.*
- *The VOC (Voice of the Customer) and its representation, found in 14 sources.*

- *Defining the difference between Perceived and Product Quality, seen across 20+ sources.*
- *The all-pervasive effect of Brand and its relation to PQ, in 20+ written works.*
- *Material that is pertinent to purely automotive, represented in 40+ items.*
- *The need in a Six-Sigma Quality tool sense to conduct an MSA (Measurement Systems Analysis) is poorly represented.*
- *The Control aspect is almost bereft of literature.*
- *A brief comparative look at other industries to see if there is any learning there to relate to automotive.*

A large number of automotive biased papers emanated from collaboration between Chalmers University and Volvo Cars in Gothenburg. These analysed the early design and specification of vehicles in minute detail, (Wagersten, Wickman, Forsland, & Söderberg, 2011) culminating in a PhD Thesis (Wagersten, 2013). This

group of people also usefully compared Japanese and Swedish product development techniques (Bergsjö, 2011). Yet more outside this group also concentrated on body and panel design (Hazra, Williams, Roy, & Aylmore, 2008).

Other researchers looked at detail of design and manufacture demonstrating good PQ by considering certain key aspects of a vehicle's features such as door closing sound (Parizet, Guyader, & Nosulenko, 2008), heater controls (Wellings, Pitts, & Williams, 2012; Wickman & Söderberg, 2010) and even the noise from engines (Nosulenko, Parizet, & Samoylenko, 2013).

Only towards the end of the main reading phase did this author find a number of connected papers on the subject of Design and Emotion and the Human-centred school of thought. Empathic design has been considered and reviewed in a UK study (Barrett, 2010) and some research in the field of HMI (Human /

Table 1. Selection of commercially available automotive quality surveys.

Survey brand or name	Method and markets
J D Power & Associates APEAL (Automotive Performance, Execution and Layout)	Examines new vehicle owners' assessments of the design, content, layout, and performance of their new vehicle after 90 days of ownership. Considers 90 attributes in 10 categories. Considers satisfaction of: Ride, handling and braking Comfort, convenience and seats Heating, ventilation and cooling Sound system Styling and exterior
J D Power IOS (Initial Quality Survey)	Assess ownership experience at 90 days and one year on. Overall Quality Overall Quality Mechanical Powertrain Quality (engine, transmission and driveline) Body and Interior Quality and Design Features and Accessories Quality and Design Overall Design Quality
J D Power DrIVE (Driver Interactive Vehicle Experience)	Considers things that go wrong or fail within the first 90 days of ownership.
VDS or Vehicle Dependability Survey	Considers: Exterior Engine and transmission Sound System and Navigation The driving experience Interior Features/Controls/Displays Heating, ventilation and cooling Seats
ALG Residual Value POS (Perceived Quality Score)	Active in most markets, including: - ASEAN, Brazil, China, North America, UK, India, Japan, Mexico. (ASEAN is: Brunei, Darussalam, Myanmar/Burma, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Vietnam).
Magazines such as What Car New Car Buyers Survey	POS aims to predict resale values of North American automobiles, derived from Canadian customer surveys.
Parkers Car Reviews	Owners' reviews, plus publishers' comments, with simple, easy to understand good and bad points.
Newspapers, such as The Daily Telegraph reviews and road tests	As above – most markets have similar tailored offerings
Motoring Associations such as the AA Car Buyers Guide	As above

Sources: 2016 websites for J D Power, ALG, What Car, Parkers, Honest John, The AA

Machine Interface) (Erol, Diels, Shippen, Richards, & Johnson, 2014). However, it was these final papers from a cluster around Delft University that finally began to coalesce what PQ is and how to look at the subject from a human and affected emotion point of view. The work in Delft has led to a recent paper on the subject of human-centred design and the proposed Product Impact Model as shown in Figure 2 (Fokkinga, S., Hekkert, P., Desmet, P., Özcan, E., 2014).

This model has been trialled by this author with a growing (30+) sample of vehicle users and found to provide useful data on the emotive aspects of car ownership, so closely associated with PQ and gives a new viewpoint on the measurement of PQ. The importance of emotion in vehicle purchase is evidenced by a BMW publication, which significantly pre-dates the model and makes many of the same emotive connections (Benson, MacRury, & Marsh, 2007). As it is hoped that the research will have some commercial use, purchase drivers are a subject close to the heart of any manufacturer.

Results

The diagram following (Figure 3) shows that the Impact Model (shown by the Design and Emotion D&E box) is a part of the many influences on PQ. It is vital for any company to survive that they attend to customer wants, by using tools such as QFD (Quality Function Deployment) and Kano (Matzler & Hinterhuber, 1998).

As observed by a Swedish industrial visit to Japanese companies, the use of such tools is seen as core to their activities in bringing product to the customer that they want to buy (Bergsjö, 2011). Nissan's own Public Relations machine acknowledges these findings (Sawyer, 2007).

Figure 3 attempts to link the Product Impact Model into a wider look at PQ and is proposed by this paper. It is created from the literature already discussed and the author's 30+ years in the automotive industry.

The results of the systematic critical literature review shows that, of the over 80 papers and works reviewed and critiqued, from a Perspective point of view, the bulk of the research (53 items) takes as expected a User viewpoint, as the subject is perception of quality. There were 10, which were classified as taking a

Fokkinga, S.; Hekkert, P.; Desmet, P.; Ozcan, E. Delft Uni. 2015

Figure 2. Product Impact Model. Source - (Fokkinga, S., Hekkert, P., Desmet, P., Özcan, E., 2014).

purely Engineering view and also a healthy crossover of 17 using both.

In terms of the metrics used in the research material, the statistics do not add up to the quoted total for the subjective (63 sources) or objective (22 sources) and qualitative (70+) or quantitative (less than a quarter), as in many cases there was a clear mix of these. As hoped, there was a strong leaning towards subjective or customer opinion.

Emotion and PQ

A search made on the word 'emotion' in the titles of the collected literature shows only four papers with the word in the title, demonstrating how poorly the current material is at considering and two of these were from the Delft University research group. The latter pair considered "Nine sources of product emotion", (P. M. A. Desmet, 2011) and a summary of Design And Emotion subjects over the last decade (P. Desmet & Hekkert, 2009).

The others looked at the emotion evoked by car engine noise (Nosulenko et al., 2013) and the effect of emotion upon our decision-making process (Bird, 2014). Samples of other subjects covered in the reading are shown below (Table 2), showing the occurrence of the words 'design' and 'emotion' in the text.

Table 2. Literature Review for the use of the words Design or Emotion found in a paper or article.

Paper subject and author	Subject mentioned	
	Emotion	Design
Sound Quality – "Brand DNA" (Abe, Clapper, McCarthy, Rubio, & Schabel, 2004)	2	2
Quality reputation (Cole & Flynn, 2009)	1	3
Seat comfort (Erol et al., 2014)	1	29
Craftsmanship in vehicle interior design (Ersal, Papalambros, Gonzalez, & Aitken, 2011)	1	70
Perceived quality and image (Homer, 2008)	2	3
Door closing sound (Parizet et al., 2008)	0	4
Critical Styling Data (Wagersten & Söderberg, 2010)	0	26
Automotive switch feel (Wellings, Williams, & Pitts, 2008)	5	30

Discussion

Literature statistics

The analysis in Table 2 shows how the researchers whose work has been evaluated thus far treat the subjects of design and emotion. Design comes out as by far the greater concern of many areas of research, with emotion trailing far behind. It is encouraging that the perspective taken by most researchers has the user or customer at the heart of the studies. There appears no shortage of subjective metrics in the material, but little quantitative measure. Planned further work with the Product Impact Model could improve this situation by providing more data to analyse, looking for trends and key words to support definition of PQ.

VOC (Voice of the Customer)

If we accept from the preceding analysis, that Perceived Quality can be measured in part by measures of product quality, then what of the other metrics to give shape to PQ? Traditional PQ is often derived from the ingredients seen earlier (Figure 1). Manufacturers have concentrated heavily on such elements as panel gaps and profiles. This is an element from product quality that is measurable and can inform the viewer of the visual impact of the car. A significant part of PQ, according to Warwick University's WM006 course 'Principles of Perceived Quality' (Warwick Manufacturing Group 2016) is VOC and methods for capturing the same, as well as looking at ways of analysing the emotional effect and the role of all the senses. This is a closed course, open only to one vehicle manufacturer. The VOC section of the Warwick course is based closely upon the work of Professor Noriaki Kano, (1984) whose simple, graphical analysis of customer needs rated execution on the x-axis and their satisfaction on the y-axis.

Professor Kano suggested that:

- Value attracts customers,
- Quality retains them,
- Innovation differentiates a company from competition.

Over time the innovation becomes accepted and even morphs into a basic need, such as has happened with free wi-fi in cafes, or sat-navs and DAB radio in cars and the process is repeated. From a 2016 point of view are dashboard cameras in cars to become the norm?

Kano also proposed that there were three key types of customer need:

1. Basic issues, such as acceptable car fuel economy or comfortable temperature in a hotel room.
2. Performance, such as acceleration of a car to keep up with traffic.
3. Excitement, such as a mobile telephone that integrates well with the car.

Although not a measure of PQ, the use of models like Kano (1984) are vital to understanding the Voice of the Customer and giving it some shape. Other techniques, such as QFD (Quality Function Deployment), much used by Nissan for example (Sawyer, 2007), takes

customer *wants* and converts these into Engineering *hows*.

The Chalmers University industrial visit to Japan showed the vital importance of QFD and addressing the VOC to Japanese companies' success (Bergsjö, 2011). Using Kano and QFD (Matzler & Hinterhuber, 1998) to further understand the customer, quality measures must look at PQ rather than what is normally claimed by the manufacturer (external) or deemed important by Engineering, e.g. standards (internal). External = subjective, Internal = objective (Stone-Romero, Stone, & Grewal, 1997). This is where the Product Impact model adds a deeper insight into measuring PQ. The effect of the ownership or user experience on the human clearly has to be taken into account and the model is a useful tool in supporting this analysis.

From personal experience of 10 companies or marques, the author has seen many different PQ scoring regimes, with each one showing similar roots if not scoring devices as the others. As the subject of PQ has developed, the methods of measuring it have grown from the basic Product Quality issues of:

- Panel Pressing Quality
- Panel and trim component Gaps and flushes (size, taper and consistency)
- Access and egress
- Operating loads
- Storage space
- Visual Impact, including colour and trim, brightwork or garnish

The preceding are still vital components, but the following are now major areas of product differentiation:

- Cabin Ergonomics
- Configurable or adaptable illumination of switches and dials
- Crash avoidance and advanced driver assistance
- Ambient lighting (a new competitive pitch, more possible with small LEDs)
- Touch-screens and mobile telephone integration or connectivity.
- The "Connected Car"

The subject of PQ grows with each new generation of vehicle and the real or anticipated needs of the user - the constant necessity to innovate to satisfy customers. The use of the Product Impact Model to measure PQ gives a difficult subject more shape, with the ability to gather focussed data, fitted into a concise model, as shown in Figure 3. It concentrates upon proven neglected areas such as Design and Emotion.

Conclusions

Perceived Quality is a major competitive differentiator for car companies. Some have arguably realised this and made what appear to be concentrated efforts to present their products in the best possible way to appeal to emotions and a desire for the latest and best.

The current commercially available PQ measures are useful, yet remain the protected intellectual property

Product Impact model as input to PQ

Figure 3. Enhanced model of PQ supported by Design and Emotion - Inter-relationship of Design and Emotion with PQ.

of those offering these products, but are recognised by the buying public. They lack an obvious emotive component.

Examining any Company's PQ measures is not easily accomplished due to confidentiality issues and an understandable desire to protect such matters. However, the writer has had experience of some ten different brands or marques of automotive product and some of these have been alluded to here.

Product Quality is but a component of Perceived Quality, as proposed by Garvin. PQ measurement and perhaps subsequent control can be enhanced by the use of the Product Impact Model, by taking a more human-centred view of a product and the engineering behind it.

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Tolerance of ambiguity - Its implications for creativity and design practice

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Abstract This paper reflects on an individual's tolerance of ambiguity and its relationship to creativity. The different ways in which people handle ambiguous situations is discussed and how tolerance of ambiguity is measured. This paper discusses the adequacy of current Ambiguity Tolerance measurement methods for the field of industrial design. We discuss how creativity and tolerance for ambiguity are integrated in a designers' life. Furthermore, the paradoxical relationship between tolerance of ambiguity as a personality trait for being creative and the statement that everyone can be creative is discussed. The paper finally presents guidelines on how to tackle tolerance of ambiguity and a proposal to make Ambiguity Tolerance measurement suitable in the field of design.

Keywords *Ambiguity, AT, Tolerance of ambiguity, Creativity, Design, Design practice*

Introduction

For designers, being creative is an ever present need and ambiguity is an ever present issue to be resolved during different stages of design. Designers encounter ambiguity in design briefs, during the conceptual design phase and within design communication among multidisciplinary team members. Thus, designers are expected to deal with ambiguity and use their creativity to overcome it. However, not much is known with regards to designers' capacity for handling ambiguous situations. If designers are able to discover their tolerance for ambiguity, perhaps they can become more aware of their creative capacity related to design tasks.

Ambiguity can be described as the uncertainty in meaning or uncertainty in intention of information regarding a particular stimulus or context. Ambiguous stimuli or contexts can be interpreted in multiple ways. It differs per individual how ambiguous situations are perceived and treated. People who have intolerance of ambiguity tend to interpret an ambiguous situation as a threat or a source of discomfort (Grenier, Barette & Ladouceur, 2005). Several studies point out that an individual's tolerance of ambiguity is an important capacity of being creative (Merrottsy, 2013). Tolerance or intolerance of ambiguity is generally considered to be a personality trait (Zenasni, Besançon & Lubart, 2008) but empirical, up to date, studies on this topic are rare. Since some sources suggest that everyone can be creative (Sanders & Stappers, 2012) and if we assume that tolerance of ambiguity is an important quality for being creatively successful, it might be interesting to find a way to measure and cultivate an individual's tolerance of ambiguity, without stating that tolerance of ambiguity (AT from here onwards) is a personality trait and the only capacity for being creative.

This paper aims to answer the following questions:

what AT measurement tools do we already have and how relevant are these methods? How are AT and creativity related? Is it possible to cultivate tolerance of ambiguity? And if so, how can we do this and will this prove that people can become more creative by cultivating this AT, as suggested by Sanders and Stappers (2012)? In this paper the topic of Tolerance of Ambiguity will be reviewed, followed with a proposal to which way it can be useful to measure designers' Tolerance of Ambiguity.

AT measurement methods

Frenkel-Brunswik (1949) was among the first to discuss tolerance of ambiguity as an emotional and perceptual personality variable. Over the past 60 years many papers on this topic refer to her research and most researchers in the tolerance of ambiguity field base their definition of tolerance of ambiguity upon her work. Frenkel-Brunswik (1949) used a cognitive test to measure AT: the Dog-Cat test (Figure 1). A picture of a dog was shown and then followed by a number of pictures representing a gradual transformation of the dog into a cat. Those who held on to the original interpretation (i.e., dog) for the longest time were considered to have lower tolerance of ambiguity (MacDonald, 1970). In the period after her research many tests became available to measure an individual's tolerance of ambiguity. Most of the AT tests are unpublished and self-report questionnaires (Furnham & Ribchester, 1995). Stanley Budner (1962) introduced the most commonly used AT measurement method, which includes 16 statements, each to be assessed on a 7 item scale. Every statement referred to the either one of the three major factors describing intolerance of ambiguity: Novelty (e.g., I would like to live in a foreign country for a while), Complexity (e.g., people who insist upon a yes or no answer just don't know how complicated things really are) or Insolubility (e.g., there is really no such thing as a problem that can't be solved). The Budner scale is used

Figure 1. 3 images from the 'Dog-Cat test', adapted from *The judgment of ambiguous stimuli as an index of cognitive functioning in aging* (p. 84) by S. J. Korchin & H. Basowitz (1956).

most frequently in tolerance of ambiguity research. This relatively old method does not seem to be substantiated by research. Although, the three dimensions are relevant for the field of design engineering if the method may be developed further. McLain (2009) also developed an AT measurement scale based upon Budner's method: the Multi Stimulus Types Ambiguity Tolerance Scale (MSTAT). He first developed the 22-item self-report scale MSTAT-I (McLain, 1993) and later on the more substantiated MSTAT-II (McLain, 2009). The MSTAT-II is a 13-item measure designed to measure AT based on five stimulus types: ambiguous stimuli in general, (e.g., I don't tolerate ambiguous situations well), complex stimuli, (e.g., I avoid situations that are too complicated for me to easily understand), uncertain stimuli, (e.g., I find it hard to make a choice when the outcome is uncertain), new/unfamiliar/novel stimuli, (e.g., I generally prefer novelty over familiarity), and insoluble/illogical/internally inconsistent stimuli (e.g., I try to avoid problems that don't seem to have only one 'best' solution). Items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Higher scores indicate higher ambiguity tolerance (McLain, 2009). MSTAT-II is considered the most adequate and up-to-date AT measurement method of this time.

AT measurement methods under discussion

Furnham and Ribchester (1995) are among two of the few researchers who discuss and question some frequently used AT questionnaires, such as Budner's (1962) method, and AT on itself. Furnham and Ribchester (1995) criticise the existing methods and explain: 'AT's very appeal may be part of its weakness. Rarely is a clear operational, multidimensional definition offered.' The ways of measuring AT range from projective techniques through cognitive and pen-paper questionnaires. Hence, it is impossible that all existing AT tests are truly measuring the same thing. When comparing different AT test, as done by Furnham et al., it is clear that there is no consistency in measuring the independent variable. Tolerance of ambiguity can be conceived, as stated before, as a personality trait, but also as a cognitive orientation, a perceptual defence, or an educational achievement (Furnham & Ribchester, 1995). The perception of tolerance of ambiguity and the context have to be defined to successfully measure tolerance of ambiguity and to be able to draw conclusions from it. Where Furnham criticises the existing AT measurement methods, he does not come up with a

new, ideal, method for measuring AT.

The most relevant AT measurement method

Although it may have been criticized, Budner's AT measurement method yields effective outcome. Therefore Budner's method is still inspirational for creating a more relevant AT measurement for measuring designers tolerance of ambiguity. Taking the construct of AT a step further, Herman and colleagues came up with 3 measurement challenges as the most frequent explanation given for conflicting findings regarding tolerance of ambiguity: weak psychometric attributes, potential multidimensionality and the impact of context on individual AT (Herman, Stevens, Bird, Mendenhall & Oddou, 2010) all related to the weaknesses of AT measurement tests as mentioned by Furnham et al. (1995). To tackle these challenges Herman et al. (2010) adjusted Budner's measure to twelve questions with four new dimensions: Valuing diversity in others, ability to change, challenging perspectives and coping with unfamiliarity (Herman et al., 2010). These dimensions are built into Budner's adjusted AT measurement questionnaire consisting of twelve questions, to be found in Appendix A.

This measurement of AT has also proven to be relevant for assessment in cross-cultural contexts. Herman et al.'s method (2010) does not state that tolerance of ambiguity is necessarily a personality trait, but also a quality or characteristic an individual can develop. This is interesting for our research since it implicates that AT can be cultivated, what we will discuss later. The AT measurement method of Herman et al. (2010) can be used to classify individuals on their tolerance for ambiguity. For example students who are interested in studying design. Since capacity or tolerance of ambiguity is a defining characteristic for success in the design field, it would be worthwhile performing AT assessments on design students to get a clearer understanding if there is a relation between for example their master track choice or course direction and their tolerance of ambiguity. Later in this paper we will discuss the relevance of measuring students' tendency for tolerance of ambiguity.

The relation between AT and creativity

There are many different definitions of creativity and there is no clear definition of creativity to be distinguished. Creativity overlaps with other psychological phenomena such as intelligence, cognitive style and personality, but is not identical to

any of them (Sternberg, 1988). According to Arthur Koestler (1964), every creative act involves bisociation, a process that brings together and combines previously unrelated ideas. A definition that is broad enough to cover all types of creative acts, whether in art, science or humor (Sanders & Stappers, 2012). In this paper creativity is tackled as the act of turning new and imaginative ideas into reality. Creativity is characterised by the ability to perceive the world in new ways, to find hidden patterns, to make connections between seemingly unrelated phenomena and to generate solutions. Creativity involves four levels: doing (motivated by productivity), adapting (motivated by appropriation), making (motivated by asserting ability or skill) and creating (motivated by curiosity) (Sanders & Stappers, 2012). Creativity is not only an individual trait, but is also triggered and stimulated by social, cultural and collective factors (Simonton, 2009). We will discuss the relationship between an individual's creativity and tolerance of ambiguity. Other factors influencing creativity will not be taken into account. We will treat AT as a capacity of creativity.

Tolerance of ambiguity is significantly and positively related to creativity. This statement is partly based on the idea that situations that require creative thinking often involve ambiguity (Zenasni, Besançon & Lubart, 2008). In many sessions to facilitate, support and provoke creative thinking, toolkits containing of ambiguous elements are used. Creativity is fostered by having a choice of spaces in which to explore (Sanders & Stappers, 2012). Triggers to stimulate creativity are almost always characterised by multiple meanings and ambiguous items in creative toolkits have proven to provoke the most useful responses. An often used example of a test in a creativity enhancing toolkit is done with a paperclip. The participant is presented with a paperclip and has to come up with as many possible ways in using it as possible. The paperclip is in this set up used as an ambiguous object (Figure 2).

Studies have also shown that individuals with a high tolerance of ambiguity have professions characterised by a high degree of freedom. Ambiguity tolerant people are more likely to be inclined toward creative fields of work. Also, tolerance of ambiguity seems to be related to personal traits and abilities that are desired in creative professions (Stoycheva, 2003). On the other hand, exercising a creative profession may develop one's abilities to cope with ambiguity (Stoycheva, 2003). This statement suggests that tolerance of ambiguity can be cultivated and triggers further investigation in this area.

Cultivating tolerance of ambiguity

The possibilities of cultivating tolerance of ambiguity

It is expected that if you can cope with the grey area that comes with an ambiguous problem definition, you tend to be more creative and come up with more creative solutions. In other words, if you are able to tolerate ambiguity, you are more likely to succeed creatively, also in uncertain or vague situations. With practice, people can develop a higher tolerance of ambiguity. Knowledge, skills and attitudes which help

Figure 2. 'Ways to use a paperclip', adapted from <http://thesecretyuniverse.wonderhowto.com>.

people to cope with uncertainties in life have always been part of humanity. This knowledge, skills and attitudes are acquired by individuals through education. Therefore, education and training that one has received are important for their tolerance for ambiguity. Empirical data confirm this expectation: university students have higher ambiguity tolerance than their contemporaries who are not enrolled in university (Stoycheva, 2010). The studies on creativity also indicate that knowledge can make it much more easy to tackle novel and complex tasks (which are ambiguous). The type of education has also an important relationship with ambiguity tolerance. Research shows that studies in arts outscore those from the business and the medical and technical universities (Stoycheva, 2003).

The question remains whether individuals who are more tolerant to ambiguity choose such creative studies or if they learn to be more tolerant towards ambiguity during their study. What we do know is that using ambiguity in a creative challenge seems favouring ambiguity tolerance more than the group adherence to structured anonymous knowledge. Stoycheva (2003) performed a study that showed that the AT difference between students in arts and students in medicine is small and statistically negligible in the first year and significant at the end of their higher education cycle. These findings indicate that the type of education as well as the expertise gained during education are important factors for the development of ambiguity tolerance (Stoycheva, 2003). The research of Stoycheva mainly suggests that it is possible to cultivate tolerance of ambiguity. This is a relevant fact in teaching at universities and especially design schools. If universities are able to teach design students a way to be more open to ambiguity, they will probably become more creative and gain better results.

Ways of cultivating tolerance of ambiguity

Now we know that it is possible to cultivate ambiguity, it is most relevant to find out how to do this. Cultivating tolerance of ambiguity will not only make us more creative, but also helps us to deal with ambiguous situations and take bigger risks. One of the universities that acknowledges the importance of tolerance of ambiguity of their students is the University of Minnesota Rochester (UMR). In their curriculum they offer a course to teach students in understanding and pushing through the tolerance of

ambiguity. Aaron Kostko, an UMR lecturer in philosophy says that “To help facilitate students’ conceptual understanding and knowledge acquisition, educators must teach students how to be able to recognise and react appropriately to ambiguous information and situations” (University of Minnesota Rochester, 2015). UMR is still working on shaping its AT cultivation course, but acknowledges its necessity. In the next paragraph some tips on cultivating a higher tolerance of ambiguity will follow.

Tips on cultivating a higher ambiguity tolerance

By combining different literature on AT, we shaped some useful tips on generating a higher tolerance of ambiguity. These tips can be used in design processes and to teach in a design curriculum. Three guidelines in making an individual more tolerant towards ambiguity and thus more creative in everyday life:

1. **Let go control.** Individuals like to feel in control over situations, projects, the things they are doing and the life they are living. If you force yourself to let go this feeling of control, you will become open to more uncertain, thus ambiguous situations. To deal with ambiguity you need to be comfortable with uncertainty. Allow yourself and the things around you to be messy. The creative process will never be structured and/or in control.
2. **Be curious.** Try to act curious in every situation. Do not take situations as they are but always look for what is behind the things that happen. Induce judgement and avoid assumptions. Try to take an open minded stance about what is happening around you. Ask many ‘why’ questions to get to the core of for example the design problem. Listen to advice and try to listen to your own voice and ‘gut feeling’.
3. **Experiment.** Try as many options and ideas as possible and play with them. Act without the complete picture and learn by trial and error. Take time and don’t try to shortcut the creative process. Do not get annoyed by too many questions and not enough answers.

We set up these guidelines by combining different literature. When keeping these guidelines in mind at the moment of -or before- facing ambiguous situations or problems, people might be able to overcome their preliminary, and perhaps, adverse reaction towards ambiguity and cope with the situation as it is. As a result, people may be able to solve problems they struggle with and find their way out of uncertain, sometimes even uncomfortable, situations. On the following section how to combine tolerance of ambiguity, creativity and applying this in the field of design will be discussed, based on the insights retrieved by this paper.

Using AT in the field of design

So far we have shown a strong and relevant link between tolerance of ambiguity and creativity and provided evidence that we can measure and cultivate AT. It is clear that in the field of design, being creative is one of the most important assets. Almost all creative people must learn to tolerate ambiguity and incompleteness for the creation of their products.

Figure 3. Master tracks of Industrial Design Engineering, TU Delft.

Furthermore, even in the field of design, there are varying degrees of ambiguity or abstraction employed. Because there are methods available to measure AT, we can use them to classify individuals, such as design students, on their capacity of ambiguity tolerance. When doing so, it is possible to spot which group needs more help to generate tolerance of ambiguity to stimulate their creative process. Moreover there is the opportunity to create groups and teams based on people’s tolerance of ambiguity. These groups could have mixed individuals with a high AT and with individuals with low AT. When doing so, we might have many different outcomes for the same problem definitions, varying from extremely creative to pragmatic. We can classify design students on their tolerance of ambiguity and connect them to suitable courses or even master tracks. For example, in the Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering at the TU Delft, a distribution between individuals could be made between the three master tracks (Figure 3) based on AT. We could state that the three master tracks are characterised by more or less ambiguous situations during their curriculum. Design for Interaction is centred around designing experiences and interactions. Embodiment is secondary to conceptualisation and thus we could say this master track faces more ambiguous design challenges. Integrated Product Design, on the other hand, is focused on embodying and prototyping the design brief rather than conceptualising and thus designers face less ambiguity during the design process. Strategic Product Design, focussing on the business context of product and service design, floats in the middle of the three master tracks when it comes to designing with ambiguity. More elaborate research has to be done on how much the three master tracks actually differ in terms of ambiguity and how the designers in the different area’s cope with ambiguity.

In functional product design, designing an ambiguous product is often not acceptable (Gaver, Beaver & Benford, 2003) but in interaction design or experience-driven design, ambiguity may be a desirable attribute. Thus, designers with low or high AT could be distributed over different tasks to tackle issues such as ambiguity, familiarity, ease of use, cognitive comfort, safety, poetic design in order to decide whether ambiguity is desirable or should not interfere with the accomplishment of well-defined tasks, particularly in safety-critical environments (Gaver, Beaver & Benford, 2003). We strongly agree with Gavers view on ambiguity: ‘ambiguity is a powerful

design tool for raising topics or asking questions, while renouncing the possibility of dictating answers. By virtue of this balance, ambiguity both offers an inspiring resource to designers and shows a deep respect for users.' (Gaver, Beaver & Benford, 2003).

Conclusions

There is still much research that needs to be done in the field of ambiguity in relation to designers' creativity. The existing methods to measure AT are almost outdated. The most relevant tool to measure AT is the 12 item scale of Herman, Stevens, Bird, Mendenhall & Oddou (2010), which is still built upon the early Budner (1962) scale. It is worth exploring a new way to measure AT in order to further explain the relation between creativity and tolerance of ambiguity in the field of Industrial Design. What we do know is that tolerance of ambiguity is not only a personality trait and that it is possible to cultivate a higher tolerance of ambiguity. With AT considered as a capacity of creativity an individual designer can be more creative when cultivating a higher AT. We can state that any designer is able to tolerate ambiguous situations or problems and thus can be more creative. We conclude with the note that tolerance of ambiguity is a valuable resource for designers. Education in this field can make a difference in cultivation of ambiguity in design students, selection or selection of students with high tolerance of ambiguity and/or support the development of tolerance of ambiguity to support their creativity.

Recommendation for further research

This paper was a theoretically reflection on ambiguity and its relation to creativity. However, further empirical evidence is needed to support our conclusions. Our future plans include the following. We plan to facilitate a creative workshop to see how the established guidelines to cultivate AT can help an individual to solve a design problem. The following research question can be answered: is it easier to solve a design problem when being more open for ambiguity? In addition, we will perform the AT measurement test of Herman et al. (2010) (Appendix A) on design students from the different master tracks at TU Delft: Strategic Product Design, Design for Interaction and Integrated Product Design to see if there is a significant difference in the students' tolerance of ambiguity between the three master directions. The following research question will be tackled: is there a significant difference in the students' AT between the master tracks? And how can we use this information to guide students towards a better study choice or during their studies?

Furthermore, we will perform the AT measurement test of Herman et al. (2010) (Appendix A) on design students in their bachelor to see if it is possible to make a more substantiated choice for their master track based on their tolerance for ambiguity. Finally, to perform these tests a new design relevant AT questionnaire needs to be developed especially for design students with questions which focuses on designers' problem solving skills, communication skills, creation skills, etc.

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APPENDIX A - Tolerance of ambiguity 12 item scale Herman, Stevens, Bird, Mendenhall & Oddou (2010)

Items included in final measure:

1. I avoid settings where people don't share my values. [Reverse Coded]
2. I can enjoy being with people whose values are very different from mine.
3. I would like to live in a foreign country for a while.
4. I like to surround myself with things that are familiar to me. [Reverse Coded]
5. The sooner we all acquire similar values and ideals the better. [Reverse Coded]
6. I can be comfortable with nearly all kinds of people.
7. If given a choice, I will usually visit a foreign country rather than vacation at home.
8. A good teacher is one who makes you wonder about your way of looking at things.
9. A good job is one where what is to be done and how it is to be done are always clear. [Reverse Coded]
10. A person who leads an even, regular life in which few surprises or unexpected happenings arise really has a lot to be grateful for. [Reverse Coded]
11. What we are used to is always preferable to what is unfamiliar. [Reverse Coded]
12. I like parties where I know most of the people more than ones where all or most of the people are complete strangers.

[Reverse Coded]

Note: All items are scored on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "1 = Strongly Disagree" to "5 = Strongly Agree" and a "3 = Neither Agree nor Disagree" option in the middle. (This scoring pattern is inverted for items followed by [Reverse Coded], above.)

The body stocking: Design aesthetics and functionality as a means for sustainable fashion and textiles

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Abstract This paper is based on a pilot study of six parents' preferences for baby clothing and their experience of value. We investigate ways in which design aesthetics, material and the senses have an impact on high use frequency aiming to understand longevity as a parameter for sustainability in textiles and clothing. We take as a starting point that longevity has a significant impact on furthering sustainability in textiles and clothing since it can be a driver on many levels, e.g. new business models, decisions made in the design phase and/or changes in use and consumption. The study applies variations of the Repertory Grid technique and Wardrobe Studies to frame a tangible dialogue enabling the parents to elaborate on personal preferences of design aesthetics and materials in baby clothing. In the analysis we use the body stocking as a common reference point for learning about reasons for high use frequency. In addition, it is exemplified how personal taste, preferences for aesthetics and experience of wellbeing may have an impact on high use frequency. Finally, the paper points to further elaboration by suggesting a (tentative) matrix structure to better understand the parameters in designing sustainable textiles and garments focusing on longevity.

Keywords *Aesthetic preferences, Longevity, High use frequency, Sustainability, Textile & clothing design*

Introduction

In this paper we investigate ways in which design aesthetics, material and the senses have an impact on high use frequency aiming to understand longevity as a parameter for sustainability in textiles and clothing. The fashion and textile industry is one of the most polluting and resource demanding industries in the world. Production of textiles and clothing demands vast amounts of energy, water and chemicals and it leads to the emission of high quantities of CO₂ and wastewater. Concurrently a growing world population leads to increasing the global production and consumption of textiles and clothing (Armstrong et al., 2014; Nordisk Ministerråd, 2015; The Business of Fashion, 2016).

In the Nordic countries more than half of the clothing is neither reused nor recycled. Instead it ends as landfill or in the incineration plant. To top it all off, large amounts of the clothes and textiles are new or hardly ever used when discarded (Nordisk Ministerråd, 2015). Interestingly, this is not exclusively to the Nordic countries, it is a global tendency accounted for and discussed in several research papers, reports and websites (Niinimäki and Armstrong, 2013; WRAP, 2015; Treehugger, 2012) This calls for radical changes in all stages of garment lifetime from design through production and treatment to recycling or disposal.

According to the European Union's Ecodesign

Directive it is proved that 80% of household and electronic devices' impact on the environment is due to decisions made in the design phase. These decisions are categorized as components, construction and energy effectiveness (Juul, 2012). In the 2015 Nordic Council of Ministers' plan of action for sustainable fashion and textiles this is compared to textiles and clothing and it is argued, but now accounted for, that choice of materials (= components), form giving (= construction) and functionality (= energy effectiveness) are parameters, which have a high impact on sustainability in this particular field (Nordisk Ministerråd, 2015). Also the consumers play a role for the environmental impact of textiles and clothing and the importance of changes in user behavior is widely acknowledged. These changes include but are not limited to less consumption, decrease of wear and an orientation towards consumption of better and more durable textiles (Nordisk Ministerråd, 2015).

Also new business models play an important role for sustainability. A recent example is circular business models (Botsman and Rogers, 2011). Presently, at Design School Kolding we collaborate with Vigga A/S, which is building on a circular business model offering a subscription service to eco-certified baby clothing (Vigga). Babies grow with such a speed meaning that they rarely wear out the garments. Therefore, the company aims to increase the longevity of the garments by circulating it between the subscribers. It is worth to emphasize that the present

study is not a study of the business model or Vigga's service in particular. It is more general in the sense that we set out to investigate ways in which design aesthetics, material and the senses have an impact on high use frequency aiming to understand longevity as a parameter for sustainability in textiles and clothing. In order to investigate this we planned a pilot study, exploring six parents' experience of value and preferences for baby clothing. In the next section we position our work within the body of theory on sustainable fashion and textiles taking a particular interest in literature concerned with longevity of clothing as a parameter for sustainability. Subsequently we introduce our research approach combining tangible means with semi-structured interviews. The analysis investigates ways in which the parents experience value of their baby clothing. Our aim is to understand ways in which longevity, understood as high use frequency, can be connected to choice of materials, form giving and functionality in order to outline a (tentative) framework for working with longevity already in the design phase.

Related work

Recently in the field of fashion and textile design a growing awareness towards sustainability has resulted in a significant increase in research (for an overview, see for example Fletcher and Grose, 2012; Fletcher and Tham, 2015; Gardetti and Torres, 2013). The Finnish researcher Kirsi Niinimäki emphasizes the importance of investigating new business thinking in the textile and clothing industry to create a change from the current, where the economic and industrial systems are interlinked with fast changing trends and high speed production (Niinimäki, 2015). Similarly, Kate Fletcher and Linda Grose (2012) suggest looking at what fashion-sustainability can offer in order to change the paradigm of fast fashion towards a more sustainable fashion paradigm by seeing sustainability as an opportunity to design and not as an obstacle.

Recently, Niinimäki has conducted questionnaire surveys to study short- and long-term use of clothes in order to explore the reasons for maintaining use and prevent an early disposal of clothes (Niinimäki, 2013). She also contributed to the research within sustainable fashion and textiles by studying product relationships and disposal of clothes. Further, Niinimäki and Koskinen (2011) argue, that a satisfying use experience can be achieved when meeting the user's expectations for quality, functionality as well as aesthetical dimensions especially when wanting to obtain long-term use (ibid., 2011 p. 182). They suggest an empathic approach to the design process by focusing on value creation (e.g. user emotions, identity construction, aesthetic needs and personal memories) to merge the user's different levels of attachment (Ibid., 2011). From a sustainable perspective, it is important to extend the functional use time of garments to save textile and energy resources and create less waste and pollution. Notable to our study of baby clothing, Niinimäki and Armstrong (2013) argue that good functionality and aesthetic aspects relating to beauty (e.g. design, style, color, and material choices) are elements creating satisfaction with clothing items that lead to use for a longer time.

Hence to foster a deep emotional satisfaction in clothing both functional and aesthetic experiences must be embraced as an active for value creation.

Niinimäki (2014) argues that the experience of clothes is much broader than only visual perception as the garment is always experienced in relation to a bodily interaction. In extension she has studied emotional experience and aesthetic dimensions of clothing in order to align aesthetic attributes with sustainable values. As values of emotional character seems to appeal more to the consumer rather than rational parameters, there is a potential to investigate these values in order to achieve a more sustainable use behavior (Goworek et al., 2013 p. 378). Niinimäki expresses it in this way:

"We must find new radical ways to create a win-win situation for both consumers and manufacturers – for all stakeholders – and for sustainable development. We need more knowledge about consumers and the consumption side to create a sustainable transformation process inside the fashion industry and business that leads to sustainable consumption practices" (Niinimäki, 2015 p. 3).

We agree with Niinimäki that more research about consumers and the consumption side is needed. Furthermore, we propose that insights drawn from questionnaires and traditional interviews may be supported and elaborated on by a qualitative study adopting an engaging and involving research approach. In this study we therefore propose to supplement the questionnaire surveys studying selected users' daily use and aesthetic preferences for baby clothing.

Research approach

Since the aim of this study is to get in-depth knowledge about the parents' preferences for and everyday use of baby clothing, we decided to include a variety of textile materials and garments as tangible dialogue tools in a series of semi-structured interviews. We did this with the intention to give the participants a direct access to verbalizing and expressing personal experiences and preferences.

Methodologically we decided to frame the interviews using a combined version of the Repertory Grid technique and a Wardrobe Study. The Repertory Grid technique originates in psychotherapy. It intends to establish a dialogue based on 'hands-on' investigation and comparison of a selection of elements. In fashion and textile design, these elements may be a selection of textiles and/or garments deemed relevant for the purpose of the particular study. Characteristic for the Repertory Grid technique is the use of triads, that is, discussing three elements at the time asking "How are two elements alike as opposed to the third?" (For an introduction see: Fransella et al., 2004). The technique opens for discussion on common ground, and helps the participant to express sensuous experiences and tacit knowledge of touch. A Wardrobe Study is a methodological approach to get insight in the participants' daily use practice of clothing. It is based on a focused study of the participants' wardrobe

asking specific questions about e.g. favorite items or the opposite. This allows for an analysis of everyday use, how the garments are perceived in relation to each other and preferences for the personal wardrobe. (For an introduction see: Klepp and Bjerck, 2012).

In recent years these approaches have been explored and further developed within the field of fashion and textile design research (Bang, 2013; Riisberg et al., 2015; Skjold, 2014). Both approaches encourage the participants to elaborate and reveal personal stories and values connected to the subject. However, in our research we didn't come across examples that directly combine the Repertory Grid technique with Wardrobe Studies. Our reason for combining the approaches was to invite to a dialogue that embraces and exemplify both sensuous experiences (the Repertory grid) and everyday use (the Wardrobe Study). Our intention is to encourage the participants to ladder and elaborate from impressions of quality, look, touch, shape, fit, details, comfort, usability and use frequency, to personal use experiences. In the analysis we use this combined approach to explore longevity of baby clothing on the three levels introduced above, namely the material, the form giving, and the functionality.

Tangible dialogue tools

The semi-structured interview allows for subjects that may arise during the conversation. Our interview is divided into three parts. Part one and two is based on the Repertory Grid technique: 1) Tactile and visual perception of textile triads and 2) Visual perception of garment triads. Part three is based on a Wardrobe Study approach: 3) Review of high, medium and low use frequency of garments in the baby wardrobe. Each part of the interview leads to the next gradually encouraging and enabling the participants to include and elaborate on personal preferences of baby clothing.

Textile triads

In this section we describe the textile triads. They were used in part one and two of the interview about tactile and visual investigation of fabrics for baby clothing. We decided to bring three triads of textiles to the interviews not knowing if the participants would have the time to do one, two or three rounds of investigation. The criteria for choosing the textiles

Figure 1. Textile triads 1, 2, and 3.

were that they were suited for baby clothing and represented nine different types of textiles (tactile as well as visual). To represent different styles, the textiles vary in surface structure, color, mélange, stripes, graphic and naive print. We decided to let a few stand out e.g. the color black. The textiles are knitted or woven in different construction techniques. Five textiles are with a pattern and four are without. All textiles are cut in a proper size for handling, each one measuring 30*30 cm. Each triad of textiles is placed in a polyester bag that differ from the textiles. The bags measure 35*50 cm.

The first part of the interview is occupied with tactile and visual perception, that is the grip, the surface structure, and the visual appearance of the fabric. The participant was first asked to describe the three textiles in the bag and subsequently imagining using the textiles for baby clothing. Open questions led the participants to describe the grip and surface by relating to other experiences, qualities, and things, that give an impression of the emotional value, that they experience by the textiles. Following this description of each piece of fabric we asked each participant to investigate the fabrics in the bag by hand using the Repertory Grid technique to pair two textiles, which according to her have one or more common characteristics, and explain how the third textile differ from the others. This part of the

Table 1. Textile triads 1, 2, and 3.

Triad 1		Material
1a	Firm pique with stripes (two colors) (mint green and grey).	Cotton knit.
1b	Sweat fabric (two sided) (dark and light grey).	Polyester knit.
1c	Corduroy with print (paws in five colors).	Woven cotton.
Triad 2		Material
2a	Interlock, small pattern (two colors) (light blue and beige).	Cotton knit.
2b	Single jersey (plain colored) (black).	Cotton/lycra knit.
2c	Thin linen with print (stars) (dark blue background with white stars).	Woven cotton.
Triad 3		Material
3a	Thin pique (ochre and cream mélange).	Cotton knit.
3b	Striped rib (two colors) (orange and mélange grey).	Cotton knit.
3c	Velour stretch (plain color) (black).	Cotton/polyester knit.

Figure 2. Interview part one: Repertory Grid, tactile and visual perception of fabric.

interview enabled the participant to further articulate and express emotional value. After the tactile investigation we asked the participants to repeat the exercise using visual perception. As it turned out the timeframe allowed each participant to investigate two of the three bags by the sense of touch as well as visually.

Baby clothing triads

To direct the discussion from tactile and visual sensation of fabric to shape and details we chose to include baby clothes in the dialogue. The clothes are divided into three categories: girls' clothes, boys' clothes and unisex clothes. Each category is a triad with three pieces of clothes. To secure a variation of qualities one garment is from the Vigga service, one garment is from a middle price range brand, and the third garment is from a more exclusive brand. All brand tags are removed to secure that the focus is on the clothes. The nine pieces of garments are selected in order to represent different visual aesthetic qualities in details, colors and form.

Figure 3. Baby clothing triads: girl clothes, boy clothes, and unisex clothes.

The second part of the interview encourages a conversation about form and details of baby clothes. Each participant explores two triads of clothes, the unisex triad and the gender specific triad, following the same procedure as described above.

Table 2. Baby clothing triads: girl clothes, boy clothes, and unisex clothes.

Girl clothes		Material
1	Long sleeved body stocking with placement print (pigment print). Ruffles at the sleeve head.	Cotton, single jersey knit (Ruffles in voile)
2	Spencer dress with small scale print and a bow.	Cotton, corduroy
3	Body stocking and dress in one. Pleats on front and button on one shoulder.	Cotton, single jersey knit and woven satin
Boy clothes		Material
1	Hooded rompers with large scale pigment print, and diagonal zipper from neck opening to right foot.	Cotton, sweat fabric
2	Long sleeved body stocking with stripes, shirt collar, buttons, and a denim pocket.	Cotton, single jersey and denim detail
3	Rompers with stripes and envelope neck top.	Cotton, single jersey
Unisex clothes		Material
1	Fully fashioned knitted blouse with mother of pearl buttons.	Wool, finer knit with rib details
2	Long sleeved body stocking with turtleneck.	Cotton, full rib
3	Rompers with feet, small collar, and diagonal opening with press studs from neck opening to right foot.	Cotton, ribbing pattern

Figure 4. Interview part two: Repertory Grid, form and detail.

Wardrobe study

The third and final part of the interview is concerned with the daily selection and use of baby clothing. The participants were asked to select three to five pieces of clothes that the baby wears often, three to five pieces that are worn occasionally, and three to five pieces that are rarely or never used.

Data

In this pilot study we interviewed six mothers of children age three to seven months, on maternity leave in order to learn about experiences, preferences, considerations, daily use and acquisition of baby clothing. The aim was to conduct the interviews in the participants' home close to the baby wardrobe. Two participants declined this and the interviews took place in a meeting room instead. The interviews lasted between 45 minutes and one hour. All interviews were audio recorded and transcribed. During the interview we took still images of the examination of fabrics and garments and of the wardrobes. All participants signed a document allowing us to use the data for research purposes. Occasionally the participants mention brand names and specific convenience stores. Since this is not the focus of the paper, we have omitted names from the transcriptions and replaced them with "X-Company" or "X-Store".

Perspectives on use practice

This study explores ways in which design aesthetics, material and the senses have an impact on high use

frequency aiming to understand longevity as a parameter for sustainability in textiles and clothing. We begin the analysis exemplifying how the participants' personal taste and preferences for aesthetics may have an impact on high use frequency even though they claim that baby clothing is mainly about wellbeing and usability. Secondly, all mothers without exception emphasized the body stocking as an inevitable and basic piece of garment in the baby wardrobe. Therefore, we continue the analysis using the body stocking as a common reference point for learning about the participants' reasons for high use frequency of baby clothing. Finally, we look briefly into the participants' awareness towards sustainability and its impact on preferences and high use frequency.

Aesthetic preferences

During the interview the participants used the textile materials and the garments in the triads to describe sensuous experiences and relate them to baby clothing. All participants elaborated on the spontaneous description and gave examples of their own preferences. Finalizing the interview with a visit in the children's wardrobes allowed the parents to further exemplify and elaborate on their preferences for and choices of baby clothing. Especially two participants emphasized in the beginning of the interview that baby clothing is about comfort and wellbeing and that design aesthetics is not that important.

A-A: For me it is important that he can move freely and that it [the clothes] feels nice against the skin. [...] Before he was born I imagined that I would care more about his clothes [aesthetically]. But now it's more important that it feels nice to wear, and that it is practical. Otherwise it doesn't matter if it is bought in a certain store or not. I don't care.

A-M: I really don't care about the look. I'm a much more practical person, also when it comes to myself. You know, it should be nice to wear and practical. Go well with the weather and so. And when that is said, I mean, when you have something, you know, when I have something that looks good I will combine it.

There is no doubt that comfort and usability is important for these mothers. Both of them emphasize this as their main preferences for choosing the baby

Figure 5. Interview part three: Wardrobe Study, functionality and use.

clothes. However, A-M also mentions that she cares about the appearance of her son. Later in both interviews both mothers reveal strong aesthetic preferences.

A-A: *I must admit that I'm not up for wild prints – like the ones from X-Company. I'm more fond of douche, classic and neutral colors. [...] I like stripes. Color combinations. And I really like douche colors. The sailor-look. I don't like it when it's too vivid.*

A-M: *Well, we have a lot with animals. Animals and plain, that's what we have. [...] I love to go with the children patterns. [...] We need animals. Colorful...*

Looking into the transcription from the interviews it becomes clear that taste and aesthetic preferences play a more significant role in the baby wardrobe than the mothers express at first. Both mothers have strong personal preferences for the look, which in the end influence the use frequency of the baby clothing. However, we also recognize the importance of the children's wellbeing and practicality in daily use.

The body stocking

All mothers in this study emphasize the body stocking as an inevitable and basic piece of garment in their baby wardrobe. We can see from the Wardrobe Studies that what is referred to and discussed as a basic garment in the Repertory Grid triads also represent high use frequency. We use this part of the analysis to exemplify ways in which design aesthetics and the experience of wellbeing and usability influence the choice of basic garments.

Basically a body stocking is defined as a top and a pair of underpants combined into one piece of garment. It opens and closes in the bottom by the use of press studs. The fabric is usually a thin jersey knitted in cotton or wool or a combination hereof. It can be plain colored, striped, printed, knitted in a certain technique etc. – but always stretchable. In our definition the bottom part of a body stocking is similar to underpants. The top part of a body stocking can be without sleeves like an undershirt and with short or long sleeves like a t-shirt. The top can have all kinds of trimmings and details such as collar, butterfly, frills, ruffles, pockets, buttons, tie-strings etc.

All mothers without exception emphasize that the body stocking contributes to comfort and wellbeing, since it prevents naked skin around the stomach and the lumbar area. This keeps the children warm and the garment stays in place when the baby rolls over or try to move in other ways. The stretchy fabric also allows the child to move freely. Furthermore, the opening/closing system in the bottom is highly functional since this makes it easy to change the diaper without having to undress the child completely. However, talking about their children's body stockings the participants express a variety of aesthetic preferences such as: large scale patterns, small scale patterns, trimmings, retro patterns, certain color ranges, certain colors, stripes, knitting techniques and materials. In general, they don't like grown-up details such as collars and pockets.

N-A prefers to have plenty of neutral body stockings: *"Because you change the baby all the time"*. In her opinion a neutral body stocking can appear in many different colors as long as it is plain and she tells us that aesthetically she prefers a certain range of dusty colors such as curry, powder, grey and cream and that chalky white is not among them. Later she tells us that she also favors a specific body stocking from X-Company, which is made of pointelle fabric. The pointelle technique creates a stretchy knit fabric in stockinette with a pattern of holes forming the design of the fabric. One of the statements R-A makes while describing the body stocking in our unisex probe kit is that: *"We definitely have plenty of these and we use them a lot"*. However, she also expresses that recently she begun to prefer blouse and trousers because her son started to eat porridge, so she changes a lot at the moment.

A-A emphasizes the color white for aesthetic reasons. In her opinion white goes with everything: *"We have a lot of white body stockings, which can be combined with different types of trousers such as jeans and striped tights etc."*. This is in contrast to A-M. She finds white body stockings very impractical because it is very difficult to clean white fabric properly when there are dry (colored) leftovers from eating on it. Furthermore, A-M often washes white garments with colored garments, because she is aware of energy use and she wishes to wash only when the washing machine is fully loaded. In her opinion this quickly turns the bright white fabric into a greyish and not so aesthetically attractive color.

It is also worth mentioning that body stockings often play a role as clothes for festivities. A-A has a body stocking with a bow tie: *"He looks very nice in that"*. She also considers using it for his baptism: *"It can be a shirt or that body stocking with a bow tie"*. Likewise, A-M shows a body stocking, which has a shirt as its upper part: *"That was a way to dress him up. I also thought it was really nice. I didn't use the top button near his throat though. Then it was still comfortable for him – also because it was a body stocking. It prevented him from having a naked stomach. [...] We used it for some weddings and his baptism"*.

The analysis of the body stocking exemplifies that depending on the grown-ups' personal preferences for aesthetics a complexity of different parameters imply high use frequency. However, we argue that this analysis indicates that high use frequency is connected to a combined whole of experiencing a favorite garment more than one single characteristic or parameter. To become a favorite garment is highly dependent on aesthetic preferences, experiences of wellbeing and usability.

Awareness towards sustainability

In the final example we are interested in preferences for sustainability and ways in which these connect with aesthetics, wellbeing and usability, which we have identified as parameters for high use frequency in baby clothing. We did not ask directly about sustainability in the interviews. We wanted the

participants to mention it if and when they felt in order to understand ways in which sustainable awareness influences in the baby wardrobe.

It turned out that all participants mentioned sustainability as an important aspect in their caretaking of the children. Sustainability is one of the key parameters in the Vigga service, which has a GOTS certification (Global Organic Textile Standard) ensuring that 95% of the fabric consists of certified organic fibers (GOTS). This standard is often referred to as the highest standard within sustainable textiles. Four of six participants are (or was until recently) Vigga subscribers. They emphasize that awareness towards sustainability was a strong reason for subscription. Especially one subscriber is very idealistic about sustainability. Two subscribers and two non-subscribers express that they frequently buy certified Oeko-tex clothing (especially body stockings and rompers) in Danish convenience stores, which are very large players on the garment market. The OEKO-TEX® Standard 100 is a common known certification of clothing signaling sustainable awareness. It is about human ecology, which *“deals with the impact of textiles and their chemical ingredients on the health and wellbeing of humans”* (OEKO-TEX®). However, with one exception all the participants are pragmatic about sustainability in relation to baby clothing. N-A expresses it very clearly: *“Somehow sustainability is kind of funny – you really want to act sustainable and at the same time you don’t want to compromise. You can say the same about organic food. If it tasted bad no one would buy it. You expect that it [the clothes] is nice and have a high quality, and then it is even better if it is organic and sustainable. But in the end, if the first two parameters are missing, it fails”*.

None of the participants express a direct interest in the specific content of the certification standards. They seem to refer more broadly to sustainable awareness when they tell us about the Vigga subscription and the Oeko-tex certification. A-A touches upon it, without clearly expressing it, when she explains that she likes second hand baby clothing because the chemicals are washed out, and thus it is healthier to wear. However, design aesthetics also have an impact on the choice as expressed by N-A: *“Now, take this body stocking, and others I have at home, from the X-store. They are Oeko-tex certified and made of 100% wool, machine washable at 40 degrees and machine dryable, which is practical. And the cream color is nice. And I think it is comfortable for her to wear this wool”*. In this example N-A combines sustainability with look, comfort and practicality.

Concluding remarks

In this study we set out to explore preferences for baby clothing in order to investigate high use frequency as a parameter for sustainability of baby clothing. We did it inviting the participants to explore a selection of fabrics and garments expressing their experiences and preferences using a variation of the Repertory Grid technique followed by an opportunity to elaborate and exemplify through a Wardrobe Study focusing on use frequency. To our knowledge this is

the first study that combines the Repertory Grid technique and Wardrobe Studies in the same interview. It is therefore worth to discuss if the combined approach was useful and contributed to the in-depth insight in preferences for baby clothing. A pilot study is not enough to draw firm conclusions on this matter but we argue that there are indications showing the potential of combining the approaches. Firstly, we can see in the transcriptions that the participants use the Repertory Grid as a starting point to elaborate verbally on (maybe tacit) sensuous experiences and that they are able to relate to and discuss personal preferences for baby clothing in general. Subsequently they use the Wardrobe Study to exemplify and further elaborate on specific preferences and use.

In the analysis we have exemplified use practice of baby clothing from three different perspectives. First we exemplified and argued for a connection between aesthetic preferences, the experience of wellbeing and usability. Secondly we looked across the series of interviews investigating and discussing different parents’ use of the same type of clothing, namely the body stocking. The examples show that even when it is about a basic ‘must-have’ garment, which is often worn close to the skin underneath other garments (for practical reasons), aesthetic preferences play a significant role for high use frequency. The examples show how much impact personal aesthetic preferences have even when it is emphasized that wellbeing and usability are the most important parameters. Finally, we discussed the parents’ awareness towards sustainability in relation to baby clothing. We exemplify that sustainability is definitely of interest when it is about the children, but it is also demonstrated how pragmatic this interest is; the choice of sustainability is constantly valued against aesthetics, wellbeing and practicality. And in general: if the parents experience that aesthetics and wellbeing does not fulfill their criteria and preferences then eco-labeling and sustainability doesn’t really matter.

Concluding the paper, the analysis indicates that the parents’ personal preferences for baby clothing is always connected to a combined whole of aesthetic preferences, experience of wellbeing and usability. Additionally, in the introduction we described the importance of acknowledging the sustainable impact made by choices in the design phase (the Ecodesign Directive and the Nordic Council’s interpretation into materials, form giving and functionality in relation to fashion and textiles). We propose to combine these parameters into a matrix structure, which can be used in the design process (Figure 6).

We suggest that the matrix have Materials, Form Giving and Functionality on the horizontal axe. This represents the parameters that are crucial to consider aiming to reach a high degree of sustainability already in the design phase. On the vertical axe is Aesthetics, Wellbeing and Usability, which we have identified as use parameters that may lead to a high use frequency and thereby contribute to sustainability in the (preferably prolonged) use phase. Furthermore, we suggest that Aesthetics is clearly connected to the

		Materials	Form giving	Functionality
Aesthetics	Parent relevant	Touch, Look	Shape, Details	Details that supports use
Wellbeing	Child relevant	Softness, Warmth	Fit	Comfortable to wear
Usability	Garment relevant	Contextual choice of materials	Cut that supports use	Daily use, Wash

Figure 6. A tentative matrix structure aimed at making choices for sustainable garment design.

parents' aesthetic preferences, whereas Wellbeing is a matter of the child's comfort. Usability has to do with the garment itself. For a start we have used the analysis to fill in the categories in the matrix with examples of possible entrance points for design of baby clothing. The idea is to further explore the matrix as an adaptable approach to secure a combined whole in designing for sustainable clothing. However, more research is needed in order to further develop and substantiate it.

Referring to companies like Vigga working with and developing business models for sustainability, the pilot study shows how aesthetics, wellbeing and usability influence the participants' choices of baby clothing and use frequency. Therefore, we argue that this tentative matrix is a contribution to further development of design for sustainability and development of sustainable business models.

Future work

As always when working with emotional value and a low number of participants we expected the study to be dominated by personal and individual stand points. We are highly aware that a more thorough user study is needed in order to substantiate the results in this paper. Likewise, we may benefit from a stronger focus on the subscription service itself in future work. For future work there are also some important biases worth to consider. First of all, the mothers are speaking as 'the parents' and on behalf of their children. Thus, it is most likely that the interviews are heavily influenced by the mothers' personal taste and thus we definitely miss an important part of the picture. Secondly, we interviewed parents from the middle class meaning that they have the economic freedom to choose what they find best for their children according to their own ideas of a good baby life. Thirdly, working with baby clothing, we faced the challenges that children up to two years grow with such a speed meaning that they will rarely wear out the garments. We decided to focus on use at one family. We still need to explore the use chain in details even though the mothers mentioned ways in which they circulated the clothes. Finally, it is worth to remark, that none of them mention high use frequency as an issue in their daily use of baby clothing or refer to it as a way to act sustainable.

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Comicubes - A playful tool to stimulate (design) creativity

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Abstract This paper investigates the play potential of an open-ended and hybrid play concept: Comicubes – a platform for play, play-testing and simultaneously tool to stimulate (design) creativity. We propose a hybrid concept that interweaves the ideas of comics and three-dimensional toys together. The concept challenges the traditional idea of comics as images that are read one after another by suggesting a more open reading paralleling the interpretation and use of and a physically manipulable toy object. The concept introduced in the paper, combines the two-dimensional serial image with a three-dimensional and therefore more open-ended toy medium – the cube. Moreover, the concept invites integration of digital enhancements in the physical plaything and thus enables potential AGE (Augmented Game Experience) elements.

Keywords *Creativity, Game, Augmented game experience (AGE), Play, Hybrid toys*

Introduction

The paper at hand introduces, investigates and tests the play(ful) potential of a concept we have named Comicubes. Our hypothesis is that Comicubes could be used as not only a hybrid plaything including elements familiar from both toys and games, but furthermore, a tool to stimulate (design) creativity.

The Comicubes concept intertwines several areas of interest to the society: play technology creativity and Augmented Reality (AR): The prototype introduced in this paper consists of 24 double-sided cardboard cubes with different information layers on the sides of each cube, including letters, words, onomatopoeic utterances and different kinds of images. Moreover, Comicubes further includes an Augmented Reality element, which may be accessed through a smart phone application.

The concept of *Comicubes* introduced in the paper is rooted in the wooden block puzzles of the past but carries a resemblance to a popular storytelling play concept of past years, namely, Rory's Story Cubes and an open-ended 'sandbox' game, *Minecraft*¹. However, despite its simple cardboard construction, our concept presents wider opportunities for more complex and interactive storytelling. Further, the AR dimension enables a straightforward connection to digital media, enabling screen-based hybrid social play (Heljakka 2016).

In conjunction with the idea of comics, this plaything evolves potentially into a toyish and/or gameful concept, which invites its user to both open-ended and hybrid play patterns. The paper continues the work of the first author with an interest in the 'the mediation of things and the thingification of media' (Lash & Lury 2007), the hybrid relations of both physical and digital toys, games and their connections to transmedia, image-based storytelling and finally, play.

Comic artists Lynda Barry and Scott McCloud have

pondered upon the nature of play. For Barry, playing is about 'not knowing'. In other words, playing presents an activity, where one is predisposed to expect the unexpected. In Barry's idea, play is 'one of the oldest, most complex, and most tightly integrated of all ecosystems' (Barry 2008, 11), which should not only be seen through the lens of fun. Adults often mix up the idea of play with happiness, but as Barry explains, there can be a kind of amnesia about the seriousness of playing (Barry 2008, 51). Through playing, we may bring something alive. A playful, imaginative take on reading comics, especially in regard to ones telling stories about characters, is crucial. If the juxtaposed images and texts created by comic artists would not be able to breathe life into their characters by activating a reader's imagination, they would probably fail on many levels.

Play is in fact a form of meta-communication, a way to express a playful state of mind. To play is to explore and to react to the world and its actors – language, images, objects and other people's behavior through our senses, cognitively and emotionally. We engage in play because it is a joyous activity, which energizes us. Sometimes playing connects with everything we do and sometimes, when a pattern of behavior is evoked by a playful object. One central aspect of toys is that they make us curious about their characteristics. In comics, what feeds our curiosity is both the personalities of characters and what happens to them as the plots of the stories unfold. Openness to interpretation intrigues the imagination when reading

1 For Rory's Story Cubes, see <https://www.storycubes.com/>. In digital games such as *The Sims* and *Minecraft* the patterns of play are open-ended as compared with the traditional notion of games as rule bound systems of play. In *The Sims*, says Stein, we can understand each instance of gameplay as constructing a narrative that the player both follows and authors (Stein, 2006, 259).

Figure 1. The Comicubes prototype box.

Figure 2. The Comicubes concept consists of 24 folded and two-sided paper cubes (or boxes), which can also be opened.

comics and playing with toys. In our suggestion, the openness of both forms of storytelling may be increased by hybridization.

Theoretical background: Play, creativity and storytelling

Together, creativity, storytelling and tangible media, stimulate creativity through play. Play has universal dimensions, but also culture-specific aspects (Smith 2010, 95). Huizinga (1992, 19) states that “Play is older than culture, for culture, however inadequately defined, always presupposes human society, and animals have not waited for man to teach them their playing.”

Huizinga defines play as voluntary activity in which people set the terms and timing of their own involvement. Second, play is distinguished from routine affairs by its absence of material consequences. Third, play is separated from other activities through its use of rules, spaces, ideas of time, costumes, and equipment. Fourth, play both honors rules and encourages transgression. Finally, play can promote participants bonding together in “secret” (Heljakka 2013, 194; Henricks 2008, 159). According to Follet (2007), play is often associated with “winning” pleasure emotions (Lieberman 1977; Zimmerman 2003). The Comicubes concept promotes play as a voluntary activity and invites one to involve in open-ended play with the material.

In Western society, ‘creativity’ is most commonly used to refer to the embodied cognitive process that gives rise to pieces of music, paintings, poems and other things that are taken or presented as art. Creativity is heavily dependent on the nature of the creator and it is also intensely context-dependent: reproducing the style or exercise of style replication. Margaret Boden (1990) introduced exploratory creativity, where the conceptual space being explored is fixed (though possibly not all visible, and possibly infinite) and exploration occurs within that space (for example, different songs in a particular style), and transformational creativity in which the space itself is subject to change (developing from one style to another). (Boden 1990) Thus, we see that the production of the Comicubes per se is not what guarantees its value: while of course, the artifact must

exist to be valued, it is interaction between production and (probably, at least initially, introspective) evaluation by a user, and then by a social user group, that identifies relative value and relative novelty, of both the artifact and the way it was made. Thus, we can decompose creativity into a series of steps and test within a process, of which a ‘creative’ agent is capable, and can begin to study it. This is altogether more scientifically tractable than the philosophical debate about the ineffable nature of creativity itself.

Stories include narratives that serve as schematic structures. According to Mandler (1984, 22), stories exist in the background, bottom, or part of a structure and remain relatively unchanged regardless of content or genre. One of the basic human means of experiencing the world is through stories. The quality of a story derives both from life and processes of reflection. Within stories, narratives serve to guide and provide a structure for a listener or reader. With regard to games, to engage in a narrative as a player is to be drawn into participating with a story (Clandinin 1989). In Comicubes the concept itself is the story and one has the possibility to create stories of one’s own by using the Comicubes concept as a playful tool.

Comicubes: A hybrid playful concept

The Comicubes concept introduced in this paper describes an experimental plaything, a hybrid combining sequential art with a physical, three-dimensional play-object, or toy. As argued earlier, it is interesting to see how hybridization has occurred in contemporary play material and applications. Hybridity may occur in many ways in a plaything. Examples of levels or dimensions of hybridity in games and toys have been explored e.g. by Heljakka (2012) and Tyni et al. (2013). When discussing the hybrid affordances of the Comicubes concept introduced in this paper, it is therefore also interesting to reflect upon its possible connections to game-like objects and play patterns associated with them. The Comicubes concept consists of two versions, A and B. In both versions of Comicubes², we utilize 24 foldable cardboard cubes with 6 sides each. Altogether, in the one-sided version this makes 144 sides, and in the double-sided version 288 sides of information layers to fill with either images (such as

photographs) or text (letters, onomatopoeic utterances or words), or, as in classical comics, juxtaposed and serial images together with text.

‘Comics is a mono-sensory medium. It relies on only one of the senses to convey a world of experience’, says McCloud (1993, 89). On the contrary, the Comicubes concept as a *multisensory* play concept also invites the reader to manipulate/rotate/organize-stack/build sequences of the parts in either random order or according to the reader/player’s wishes.

‘Playing is about not knowing’, claims Lynda Barry (2008). Hypothetically, Comicubes, as a multi-sensory play medium, affords various play patterns: it allows the player to explore, organize and display it like building blocks; to arrange, rotate, stack and display its pieces by animation of the player’s hands. Compared to animation which is sequential in terms of time, comics are spatially juxtaposed (adjacent, side-by-side) (McCloud 1993, 7). The images and texts and combinations of them in each frame and side of a cube allow both an animated manipulation, juxtaposed arranging of them and in this way, nonlinear narrative construction. Instead of being an *automaton*, an object presenting autonomous movement, or a pre-animated experience, the Comicubes require actions associated with *object play* (see e.g. Smith 2010), i.e. tangible exploration. In other words, the player gives movement to the object and through his/her act of play decides the arrangement of these sculptural (cardboard cube) pieces.

The Comicubes, as seen from the perspective of this paper, is a research instrument and potential playful tool that may stimulate creativity, which allows exploration of dimensions of its playability, play patterns and play value. Through a test pilot study, described in this paper, we seek answers in order to understand both the nature of the envisioned concept and the processes, which evolve around it, once put into play. We suggest that the Comicubes concept invites the user to play with it and can therefore be seen as a potentially playful object. Further, the Comicubes gives the comic story a toyish dimension and thus more narrative openness than a reader of a traditional comic is used to. Moreover, this transfiguration brings into discussion both the affordance and the play-value of the proposed object, the potential plaything.

Hypothetical play patterns of Comicubes

The Comicubes come packaged in a cardboard box (Figure 1), which can also be used to arrange the cubes. On the other hand, and contrary to the idea of a traditional puzzle, the cubes should also invite to play happening ‘out of the box’, outside of the grid constituted by the frame of the box. Moreover, as an artefact aiming at as open patterns of play as possible, the Comicubes should also invite to play that does not involve all 24 cubes, but perhaps only a few of them, paralleling the idea of a short comic strip that only utilizes some frames to tell a story. In this way, this exploratory ‘comic-toy’ does not restrict itself to a strict 3D format that would run its course in one glance or purely visual engagement. Instead, the

artefact invites its user to manipulation, exploration and otherwise imaginative reception – in other words – invites the recipient to playful engagement with itself offering a new way to experience elements constituting several potential stories in 24 pieces. At the same time, the toyishness and play-value should be communicated on the level of one Comicube only, whereas the storyness is enriched by adding more cubes to the player chosen and constructed set.

There are many ways to manipulate the cubes. Movement is essential in how the player will access the images and texts displayed: The player may ‘read’ one cube at a time, moving from one side of the cube to another, simultaneously turning around the cube. Alternatively, one may organize the cubes either in horizontal or vertical arrangements, in formations familiar from comics; ‘strips’ or panels, by creating series of frames consisting of any number of cubes between 2–24.

We have constructed an introductory video presentation about some of the hypothetical play patterns the Comicubes concept holds (see: <http://youtu.be/sRGss4sVF-4>).

Toyish playability: Open-endedness

De Valk et al. have explored open-ended play with interactive objects in multiple studies (see e.g. de Valk, Bekker and Eggen 2013). According to their studies, open-ended play provides a player with the freedom to construct his/her own rules, goals and meaning. Thus, open-ended play designs offer interaction opportunities as a trigger for creating personalized games. We must keep in mind that even ‘seemingly limitless open-play scenarios, include implicit or explicit rules that establish behaviour’ (Flanagan 2009, 252). In other words, eventually, rules are even created in open-ended or toyish type of play.

The open-endedness of Comicubes limits itself on one hand in terms of its physical dimensions. On the other hand the visual and textual information in the frames of the cubes is equally limited. However it is in the creativity and playful attitude of the reader to decide where the limits for arranging the cubes are. In other

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- 2 One their one side, the 24 Comicubes in the first prototype come with six comics ‘stories’ divided in the following themes; 1) The history of comics, 2) The history of toys, 3) Onomatopoeia (classical examples from the history of comics), 4) The dancing doll, 5) A toy comic developed by the concept designer of Comicubes and 6) Arguments from this research paper articulating, explaining and developing the concept. The colouring of the ‘photoplay’ (toy photographs) is toyish in nature, whereas the argumentation follows a more subtle tone. One their reverse side the 144 frames come with either a letter of the alphabet or a key word. In this way, the reverse side of the Comicubes affords to be played like a more elaborate set of alphabet blocks.
 - 3 “Every successful children’s action fantasy, like Pokémon, like Superman, is also an organizing fantasy”, see Jones (2002, 223).

words, Comicubes is constrained in its design due both to its materiality and capacity to communicate visual and textual clues.

How does Comicubes differ in its artefactuality and openness to play as compared to for instance a puzzle or a brainteaser? A classical puzzle, a jigsaw, usually builds up around the idea of one correct solution, one that is most often communicated visually on its packaging. We may see this visualization as the fundamental explicit rule of how to 'play' in the right way. On the other hand, a traditional jigsaw puzzle, due to the form of its pieces can only be assembled in one way without breaking the pieces. On the contrary, the Comicubes does not require its parts to be assembled in any particular way. Nor does the concept require the reader to use a regular die or any other device in order to decide the order of cubes. Of course, this does not exclude the option of using additional elements such as other toys or objects, however, if the player so decides. Although the cubes can be organized in any way the player decides, the designed affordances are built upon the idea of the human tendency and desire to see meaning in structure and organizing. This parallels to what Jones (2002) calls 'organizing fantasy' known from the actions of collector-type players who get enjoyment from both the arrangement of their collected objects (e.g. creating displays) and in their minds, building up a data bank of information about these objects found in various sources, e.g. in the realms of fandom.³

The Comicubes box, which functions both as a storage space for the plaything(s) may also be seen as a frame, a Huizinga magic circle of play that both signals 'this is a thing to be played with' and communicates the affordance of using it to organize and reorganize the cubes in seemingly endless combinations of the 24 cubes and their two sides, which means 6⁴⁸ (over octillion) different combinations to be more precise. The player may only use some of the cubes in order to create comic strips, or play with the complete set by using the either the sides of a particular comic 'series' or by mixing them.

Gameful playability: Constructive co-operation
'Gaming is people-oriented' (Ståhl 1987, 16) and many forms of play are enjoyed because of the social aspect. As the number of players who may manipulate and organize Comicubes simultaneously is not restricted in any way, the concept can be situated either in the categories of single-player or multiplayer and thus social, even co-operative play. As such, the concept differs from traditional comics, which are usually read by one reader at a time. When considering their physical dimension, toys are traditionally not seen as socially shared objects as compared to e.g. board games. Instead, two players may play in parallel with similar toys.⁴ However, as a potentially shared plaything, Comicubes presents the possibility of collective and co-operative play in the name of open-ended, non-linear storytelling, providing the players with a visual, narrative and tactile, multiplayer play experience. As a conceptual platform, Comicubes is also a content distribution device, allowing different character licenses and their various

story worlds to be used. Moreover, the possibility of seeing Comicubes as a *construction toy* opens up new ideas on potential ways of organizing the cubes and categorizing it as a hybrid plaything featuring familiar characteristics of both puzzles and building blocks.

Games are fundamentally experiential, explains Mary Flanagan (2009, 184). Ståhl divides games into entertainment games, educational games, experimental games and research games (Ståhl 1987, 34). We assume that the Comicubes concept is not only a potential hybrid between comics and toys, but also a hybrid of an experiential and research type of a *game* (system). Experiential games aim at testing theories or hypotheses without having an application in mind. It is because of its hybridity that the Comicubes concept is experiential. In other words, without play testing it, it is impossible to understand and to report to outsiders what the players think of it in terms of a playful object about its play value, *playability* and possible unexpected affordances. On the other hand, the concept can be potentially understood as a research game, a game 'with the purpose of obtaining empirical material'. When test-played and documented, this potentially playful artifact will also generate empirical material that can be later applied in designing new toy/game experiences.

Hybrid playability: Augmented Game Experience (AGE)

Hybridization between forms of entertainment media has interested scholars of various playthings, both digital and physical. In recent times, games have made an entry to numerous other forms of entertainment and areas with more utilitarian functions. Gamification, as a sub-phenomenon of the *ludification* and parallel to the emerging *toyification* of culture (Heljakka 2014, 2015), refers to the application and use of game elements in 'apps' outside of the gaming context.

MR (mixed reality) systems cover the extensive continuum between reality and virtual reality (Azuma 1997, 20). In practice, MR (mixed reality) systems are implemented as AR (augmented reality) systems, in which a real world environment is augmented with digital (virtual) objects, or as AV (augmented virtuality) systems, in which a virtual environment is augmented with real objects. As a result, AR or AV systems use user interactions with both real and virtual objects to enhance user perceptions and experiences (Tråskbäck, 2004, 13). The concept of the Comicubes could create digital content, which extend storytelling to next level. Augmented reality technology give great possibilities to open virtual world for one side of the comic, which can be anything for example a picture, alphabet, sign or QR code. And using camera phone with augmented reality application you can open the virtual world and get your story for next level. The digital content could

4 For 'parallel play' see Smith, P. K. (2010) *Children and Play*, Wiley-Blackwell, United Kingdom and Parten, M. (1932) "Social participation among preschool children", *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 27, 243—269.

Figure 3. The Comicubes offer a platform for potential AGEs.⁵

be a 3D picture, video or animation.

By adding an AGE (augmented game) element to Comicubes it may become a hybrid multiplatform plaything that acts between material and digital worlds. Concretely this means that the cubes can be read by a mobile application, which scans the edges of the cubes and takes the user to different digital environments. This added material can be for example videos, music, photographs, text and/or links. It may be even possible for Comicubes users to first document and then communicate with each other using this application and share their experiences and creations. The possibilities that this digital addition creates are limitless and promising.

Method

Experimental design

As Engeström (2006) observes “play can be employed as a method in design. For example, playful techniques can be used to study users and conceptualize the idea of a new product. These techniques may include diary keeping, storytelling, scenario building, and creating visual collages. A future product may be visualized using drama, cartoons, short movies or toys.” When developing the Comicubes hybrid play concept solely for entertainment, or with ulterior motives such as co-creation, social experience or emotion experience and feedback, designing an enjoyable experience remains one of the most important aspects. In the evolving area of the gamification development in the context of creative education, finding new challenges for creativity processes has recently emerged. The aim of our pilot study was to introduce the Comicubes concept as a creative tool for users and to find out more about its potential to function first as 1) a toy, 2) a game and 3) a hybrid of the aforementioned and second, as a tool for stimulates (design) creativity.

Participants and play testing

The Comicubes concept was tested with a group of students. There were totally 9 participants (4 female and 5 male), all of who have played board games. Our participants’ age distribution was between 21 to 37 years. All participants are students at the University of Turku.

We designed the following experimental setup as illustrated in Figure 4. The subjects first got

Figure 4. Experiment Setup for this study.⁵

conditioned to a certain level of understanding Comicubes. Then the testers assigned to create their own model of the concept. They chose the technique by using equipment (scissors, markers, white/blank cubes) and created their own version of the Comicubes concept. Two researchers and one assistant operated the experiment. One guided the subjects in the role of giving lecture on play-oriented design and giving the assignment, and other undertook the interview (gave instructions for filling survey) observed the situation and ensured a stable treatment throughout the experiment. During the experimental task data was collected using video recording when users played with the Comicubes. In every step of the experiment, the time was tracked but time constraints were not imposed on subjects.

The two phases were carried out during two days. On the first day the students participated together in a lecture on playful design, which introduced the concepts of toy, game and hybrid. The students then were given the individual task of creating an individual play concept of their own consisting of four cardboard cubes.

The students needed to fill out a preliminary survey. After filling out the preliminary survey, users underwent the main test. The study was conducted in two phases: First, the students completed a design task by designing their own, individual play concept based on cardboard cubes. After the user test, participants filled out an evaluation form. Second, the students were given the task to, in pairs, interact with the original Comicubes prototype and to evaluate its play potential and play value by answering structured questions and listing all possible play patterns that

5 To communicate the possibility to use AGE enhancements for Comicubes, the prototype has been given an information layer by using Qualcomm Vuforia for Unity. In order to unlock the embedded information, a mobile application is needed

came to their mind while exploring and manipulating the cubes for 10 minutes. The results of the questionnaire are demonstrated in the following.

Initial results of the pilot study

The Comicubes pilot user test final evaluation sheet has 5 separate parts. The first part evaluates the practical benefits of the concept, which focused on its potential as a creative tool. The second part evaluates the concepts adaptability to function as a social co-creation tool, which is at the same time an individual tool for user. The third part evaluates Comicubes diversity for using the concept as professional peoples’ creation tool or as one a user could add other material like toys to. The fourth part evaluates the manageability of the Comicubes with users’ skills in playing. The fifth part of the evaluation sheet includes open questions.

In the first part, we wanted to know how the participants experience the concept’s practical benefits. We have three statements, from which the user needed to choose the best to describe their opinion. We have used a five-point Likert-type scale, which is used to measure attitudes using the following options: Strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree, strongly disagree. As such, the scale purports to measure direction (by agree/disagree) and intensity (by strongly or not) of attitude.

According to Albaum (1997), with some questions regarding attitudes, a person must compute an evaluative judgement, whereas, with others, such a judgement is simply retrieved. In a real sense, we can view an opinion a verbal expression of an attitude, which means that opinions are the means we have for measuring attitudes (Albaum 1997).

In the *first part*, the assumed practical benefits include that the Comicubes concept provides a real benefit to creativity training, in promoting creative thinking, for example the implementation of users’ creativity. The first part includes some open questions: Is it easy to create own Comicubes hybrid concept?, What things do you like mostly Comicubes hybrid concept design? Did Comicubes hybrid concept designing respond your expectations?, Could you actually play or use Comicubes hybrid concept in your studies or research to support your work? The *second part* we have claims on Comicubes hybrid concepts (Empirical findings of claims is shown Table 1.). The third part discusses which are the main user groups to use the Comicubes hybrid concept. The *third part* also discusses how participants did share their Comicubes hybrid concept ideas with other users.

Results show that the participants of the pilot testing phase of the Comicubes hybrid concept mostly say that the making of the concept was easy. Participants

Table 1. Empirical findings of claims on this study.

Arguments	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither disagree nor agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Practical benefits					
I think that I could play and take advantage of this Comicubes hybrid concept in regularly.	22,2%	22,2%	22,2%	22,2%	11,1%
I think that Comicubes hybrid concept is too complicated.	44,4%	44,4%	0%	11,1%	0%
I think the Comicubes hybrid concept is easy to understand and play.	0%	22,2%	22,2%	44,4%	11,1%
Adaptability					
I think the different functions of a Comicubes hybrid concept are connected to each other successfully and the digital dimension has been utilized.	11,1%	55,6%	33,3%	0%	0%
I believe that most will learn to use and exploit the Comicubes hybrid concept containing a digital dimension as well quickly share content on the Internet (social media)	0%	22,2%	44,4%	11,1%	22,2%
Diversity					
I think the Comicubes hybrid concept is suitable for children.	0%	0%	00%	50%	50%
I think the Comicubes hybrid concept is idea for working as a tool in the creative industries.	11,1%	0%	11,1%	44,4%	33,3%
Manageability					
I felt very confident in designing and playing Comicubes hybrid concept.	0%	33,3%	0%	33,3%	33,3%
I think learning to use the Comicubes hybrid concept requires additional guidance.	11,1%	22,2%	22,2%	22,2%	22,2%

Figures 5, 6 and 7. Students test-playing Comicubes: “Are the rules somewhere in here?”; “If this is a game, who wins?”; “This is a research-cube-puzzle-comic”.

also see that developing an idea into a prototype is easy, but *“the emergence of ideas was easier than turning them playable format”*. Participants liked most the development of their own concepts visual, using their creativity and designing for comics. Participants see that, *“its limitations, the paper and the build blocks really gave impetus to work, “what these can do?”*. Result show that participants didn’t have many expectations of the Comicubes hybrid concept. Participant’s comments include that *“there were no expectations. Slightly disconcerting was that what this even is. Is this some kind of technique to create new ideas for games and toy design of an overseer?”* Participants see that they could easily to use Comicubes hybrid concept for their hobbies, studies and maybe even work. Participants see, that one *“could image using it for a training course, but not my studies or work in this moment”*. The result of Comicubes hybrid concept claims summarized in Table 1, which provides a suggested outline of empirical findings.

Results present that participants understand the Comicubes hybrid concept as a multifunctional platform. Participants found that different combinations and the play scenarios in relation to Comicubes could be presented in a social media environment. Participants stated that if the idea is good than they could introduce their concept in social media. Participant present that *“I would introduce the concept because I, in any case make videos about playing. Implementation would be anonymously on YouTube, without the player into anyone’s identity is revealed”*. Participants present that the main target group of the Comicubes hybrid concepts are: children, students, innovation hunters, researchers and artists. Participant’s comments also included, that this Comicubes hybrid concept *“seems to be some kind of Game Jam –brainstorming technique”*.

Conclusions

In this paper, we have introduced the first version of the concept for the hybrid play instrument called Comicubes which combines and creates a mash-up of comics and toys, but also seems to be a hybrid of an open-ended storytelling device, a construction toy (or puzzle) and an experimental and research type of a game (system). Furthermore it may be considered a tool that stimulates creativity. We acknowledge the playability and play potential of the initial physical prototype, as it allows comic-style storytelling to extend itself over previous boundaries of its traditional format and in this way opens up new

possibilities for open-ended play usually associated with three-dimensional toys. Furthermore, we see potential added play value in reference to AGE elements, which can be added to the cubes graphically and read from them digitally through the use of mobile applications.

According to the results of our pilot study conducted with 9 university students and the presented analysis, it is possible to say that new elements for example digital platforms, augmented reality technology and other social media services could easily be added to the Comicubes concept. Participants liked the idea that Comicubes offers the possibility of being used simultaneously by multiple users. This could extend to experiences related to challenge and social experience, as using social interaction is the driving force in gameplay, which Comicubes also envisions. Preliminary results indicate that a combination of pleasurable and creative elements causes a sense of deep enjoyment so rewarding that participants feel that manipulating Comicubes is considered a concept one may simply enjoy in order to have a creative experience. Additionally, an important precursor to a playful way to create Comicubes is to match between a person’s creating skills and the challenges associated with the task, with both being at a certain level. Most flow or immersion experiences occur with activities that are goal-directed (as in this user test), bounded by rules, and require mental energy and appropriate skills. The study’s participants felt that creating Comicubes concepts offered them stimulation and a surprising way to create a concept of their own. How much of the enjoyment associated with the use of Comicubes, besides its gameful qualities, is dependent on its open-ended – or toyish – nature needs further assessment.

In future research we will investigate more deeply the design implications for our conceptual playful tool, presented in this paper.

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Meaning of product meanings: A classification based on theoretical perspectives

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Abstract Product meanings may have many connotations depending on which theoretical perspective is hold. A considerable amount of research has been conducted on theories of psychological responses to products. However, less attention has been paid to relate product meanings to theoretical foundations of theories. Current study is an early attempt to classify product meanings according to their theoretical foundations of major theories (Affordance Theory, Product Semantics, Product Emotions) on the topic. Descriptions and definitions of product meanings that are introduced by these theories are explored. These descriptions and concepts are emerged in three broad categories of product meanings. Consequently, the classification based on theoretical perspectives can reduce complex nature and information of the topic and guide methodological strategies for design for meaning.

Keywords *Product meanings, Theoretical perspectives, Affordances, Product semantics, Product emotions*

Introduction

Products are no longer designed only for sustaining their physical durability (You & Chen, 2007). They are designed also for leading positive experiences that are resulted in meanings and emotions associated with the product. Hence, companies have recognized that positive experiences are key to the success of a product, while a negative experience guarantees dissatisfaction with a product (Kuniavsky, 2003). Whether the meaning is associated with positive or negative experience, it is evident that designers develop products in order to communicate through certain meanings and emotions to offer particular experience. As a result, physiological responses to products have become subject to research. Products have been expected to be functional. Hence, product experience and meanings have been associated with affordances and utilitarian features of the products (Gibson, 1977; Norman, 1990). However, it is not satisfactory or acceptable when a product is difficult to use (Jordan, 2000). Krippendorff (1989a) states, *"The slogan 'form follows function' thus implies abstracting the ordinary user out of the equation and discarding the meanings that users construct and see"*. According to Desmet and Hekkert (2007), product meanings along with aesthetics lead to an emotional experience of a product; and therefore, they are significant. Users should interact with the product over time, multiple exposures in order to build these experiences (Csikszentmihalyi & Eugene, 1981; Norman, 2004). There are many theories proposed to describe physiological responses to products. These suggestions have mostly focused on Affordance Theory (Gibson, 1977), the basic communication model of Product Semantics (Krippendorff & Butter, 1984), the Product Emotion model (Desmet & Hekkert, 2002) or sensorial product experiences. Studies founded on these theories investigates many aspects of product meanings and allocates diverse methodological

approaches. However, the relationships between theoretical foundations and their concept of product meanings remain unclear. The current paper offers a brief review and analysis of the literature on theoretical perspectives of aforementioned theories and studies on the topic. It particularly focuses on descriptions and definitions of "product meaning" that each theory and study proposes. Consequently, the paper aims to classify product meanings according to associated theoretical foundations and it argues whether certain product meanings can be related to certain theories. First, the paper introduces a brief review on theoretical perspectives on perception study in next section where the evolution of perceptual theories are presented. Afterward, Affordance Theory, Product Semantics, Product Emotion Models are organized according to their theoretical foundations. Second, concepts of product meanings that these theories propose is explored. The last section introduces proposed classification and offers discussion on the topic.

A brief review of theoretical perspectives on perception

Theoretical perspectives are deliberated according to their assumptions on the matters of human (in our case, user), environment (product) and their relationship (Guba & Lincoln, 1998; Patton, 1990, 2002). Therefore, it is essential to discuss the ontological, epistemological and methodological assumptions of theories perspectives in general. Guba and Lincoln (1998) frame the main ontological questions as: *"What is the form and the nature of the reality and what is there that can be known about it?"*. An epistemological question is stated as *"What is the nature of the relationship between the knower or would-be knower and what can be known?"*. The answer of epistemological question is constrained by the answer given to ontological question (Patton, 2002)

and answers given to these two questions guide researchers to response methodological questions of “How can the inquirer go about finding out whatever he or she believes can be known?” in other words: “How should we study the world?” (Guba & Lincoln, 1998).

The debate between theoretical perspectives on the topic is rooted whether users’ response to environment is an innate biological inheritance that is based upon our ability to adapt to environment for survival, or it is a result of our cognitive abilities, social interactions and cultural context (Crozier, 1994). Theories seeking the reality from physical environment and its qualities, suggest that our psychological responses are an innate reactions and behaviors driven by the environment. These perspectives are generally inherited from Cartesian tradition and have a sharp distinction between “the world” and “the mind” (Heft, 2003). However, according to Heft (2005), the sharp separation between “the mind” and “the world” limits our capabilities to convey qualities of cognitive experiences. Correspondingly, Patton (2002) holds a constructivist approach and proposes that our understanding is influenced by the context and developed through the interaction among people; therefore, there is not a stable and individual reality. There are attempts to bridge the gap between “the mind” and “the world”. Morgan and Smircich (1980) proposes a continuum scale of theoretical perspectives in which they represent the debates between “objective” and “subjective” approaches in terms of their ontological, epistemological and methodological assumptions (see Table 1). According to them, “objective form of knowledge that specifies the precise nature of laws, regularities, and relationships among phenomena measured in terms of facts” whereas “subjectivist view of reality is a projection of individual imagination and it emphasizes the importance of understanding the processes through which human beings concretize their relationship to their world”. Although Morgan and Smircich (1980) outline ontological and epistemological differences between perspectives, they avoid directly associating methodological approaches to theoretical perspectives since research methods

might have diverse applications among different theoretical perspectives. As the continuum is observed from left to right epistemology shifts from closed mechanic conception of the world to an open system, a living organism (Morgan & Smircich, 1980). Van Rompay (2008) on the other hand investigates Gestalt school of thought -the whole is more than the sum of its parts- studies of Arnheim (1974, 1977), Koffka (1935), Dewey (1934), Merleau-Ponty (1962) and emphasizes the importance of interaction between perspectives where the emphasis on “object ” and “subject” is equally significant. Correspondingly, Almquist and Lupton (2010) suggest a common ground – an interaction– between objectivist and subjectivist approaches. The separation is also observed in the field of sensation and perception. A “bottom-up” perceptual approach indicates that physical qualities of the environment drive the perception. In this case, perception is the information that the world contains and therefore it is the source of knowledge. A “top-down” perceptual approach, on the other hand, advocates that the source of the knowledge is our ability to interpret and construct the world. This approach suggests involvement of high-level cognitive processes such as memory, knowledge, experience, analyses, synthesis and evaluation in order to establish perception (Coren, et.al. 2004; Goldstein, 2009; Sternberg, 2008). Consequently, in one hand knowledge is seen as a concrete structure and the information that environment or products contain in which users can only response to (the world-based, objective or bottom-up approach); on the other hand the source of the knowledge is a projection of human mind (the mind-based, subjective or top-down approach). Current study prefers using terms “bottom-up” and “top-down” due to their inclusive definitions and acceptance in perception studies.

Several theories have proposed to describe psychological responses to environment or products in design literature. Prospect and Refuge Theory by Appleton (1975) suggests that environment provide significant opportunities for the user who cannot consciously observe them. Main promise of this theory is that the user is a consciousness being who has innate skills to make sense of what environment offers

Table 1. Objectivist and subjectivist debates and network of basic assumptions: the continuum scale.

	Objectivist Approach			Subjectivist Approach		
Core Ontological Questions	Reality as a concrete structure	Reality as a concrete process	Reality as a contextual field of information	Reality as realm of symbolic discourse	Reality as a social construction	Reality as a projection of human imagination
Assumptions about Human Nature	Man as a responder	Man as an adaptor	Man as an information processor	Man as a an actor, the symbol user	Man as a social constructor, the symbol creator	Man as a consciousness being
Basic Epistemological Stance	To construct a positivist science	To study systems, process, change	To map contexts	To understand patterns of symbolic discourse	To understand how social reality is created	To obtain phenomenological insights
Research Methods	Lab experiments, surveys	Historical analysis	Contextual analysis of Gestalten	Symbolic analysis	Hermeneutics	Explorations of pure subjectivity

Source: Adapted from Morgan and Smircich (1980)

(such as when finding a safe place to sleep or hide). Gibson (1977) defines these opportunities as affordances. According to his Affordance Theory, also known as direct perception or ecological approach, the user analyzes cues in the environment or on the product in order to relate, compare and find relationships between other products or environmental elements. Even though the stimulus on the receptors changes, there are invariant and stable qualities of the environment such as physical size, form or distance. These qualities are called affordances "...*action possibilities afforded or available to observer...*" (Coren et al., 2004). Affordances are the features meaningful for the user even though these features are not directly related to the user or a product but more affiliated to the relationship between them (Heft, 1988). Norman (1990) associates affordances with "*fundamental properties (of products) that determine just how the thing could possibly be used*". According to him, affordance of a product should match with the function of the product and the feedback it affords to provide. Consequently, affordances are fundamental information that products contains and therefore the theory might be considered under bottom-up approach and fit under objectivist end of the continuum scale (see Table 1).

The debate opposing bottom-up theories is formed around that they lack explanation on the effects of context, expectations, knowledge, and prior experience of users. In order to accommodate the complexity, theories evolve. Semantic features of products have been studied by many researchers (Blaich, 1982; Butter, 2012; Demirbilek & Sener, 2003; Hsiao & Chen, 1997; Krippendorff & Butter, 1984; Krippendorff, 1989; You & Chen, 2007). Krippendorff and Butter (1984) and Monö (1997) apply Shannon's (1948) Basic Model of Communication to design theory and describe meaning attribution process during the design process. Krippendorff and Butter (1984) define Product Semantics as, "...*a study of the symbolic qualities of man-made forms in the cognitive and social contexts of their use and the application of the knowledge gained to objects of industrial design*". According to Buchanan (1993) product semantics is a concept that associates symbolic meanings of products to their use in context. It is an ability for a product to self-explain itself. Product Semantics includes designer as a product form generator and meaning attributer, product form as a medium that carries a meaning or a message, and the user as a receiver of the embedded meaning. Product Semantics suggest that users' context and cognitive abilities are as significant as the product's physical qualities. However, Krippendorff (1989) defines meaning attribution process as a cognitive effort and a product of the context: "...*meaning is a cognitively constructed relationship. It selectively connects features of an object and features of its context into a coherent unity*". Product Semantics consider symbolic qualities of products in diverse contextual conditions. In this case, concept of meaning refers to many connotations depending on the context of use (operational-context), user-user interaction (socio-linguistic context), interaction between developers of a product (context of genesis), and technological influence (ecological context)

(Krippendorff, 1989). Correspondingly, Monö (1997) mentions four semantic functions of products. First, a product should "describe" its purpose, the way it functions and is used. Second, a product should "express" its value and character, then it should "exhort" users to react in a specific way. At last, a product should "identify" its origins, category, and personality. Product Semantics can be considered a bottom-up approach since it values affordances and physical qualities of products. It can be also considered under top-down approaches since it also considers influences of social context and human cognition. Studies under Product Semantics can be then placed at middle area on Morgan and Smircich's (1980) continuum scale.

Developments in the fields of cognitive sciences and cognition has received favorable attention in design fields. Sanders (1992) proposes that products should be first designed based on certain needs (usefulness), then user should understand how to use the product easily (usability), and last user should desire to own and use the product (desirability). According to Jordan (2000), users profits from products in three levels: practical, hedonic and emotional benefits. A large body of research is framed around Model of Product Emotion by Desmet and Hekkert (2002). The Model of Product Emotion suggest that product is an appealing object which user can like or dislike. Emotional reactions towards to products are appraising and evaluative processes where users' concerns matters. If concerns and the product features matches, then the user may most likely love the product (Desmet, 2003). According to this approach, meaning is the source of an emotion (Schifferstein, 2010). Many advocates that concept of product meaning is a result of pleasurable and satisfying usability experience (Desmet & Hekkert, 2002; Jordan & Macdonald, 1998; Jordan, 2000; Tractinsky, 1997). Graumann (1974) indicates phenomenological aspects of meaning attribution and advocates that a product may have diverse meanings over a time even though it stays as the same product. This exposes the complexity of meanings and meaning attribution processes. As a result, studies related to Product Emotions can be positioned more close to subjectivist end of the continuum scale as a top-down approach.

Complex and inclusive theories are generated to provide a holistic view on product-human interaction and meaning attribution. Norman (2004) offers three levels of interaction that defines users' psychological responses to products: Visceral, behavioral, and reflective. Initial reactions to physical qualities and sensorial experiences occurs at the visceral level at first sight of the product. The satisfaction of effective use, performance and high usability appears at the behavioral level in which the user actually interacts with a product in relatively long time. The pleasure of the total experience of a product reveals at the reflective level when the user keeps a product and uses it over a time. Similar to Norman's approach, Crilly, et. al. (2004) suggests behavioral, cognitive and affective responses to products; Cupchik (1999) proposes sensorial/aesthetic, behavioral/cognitive and personal/symbolic responses; and Baxter (1995)

indicates intrinsic, semantic and symbolic responses to products. It can be inferred from these studies that product meanings reveal at each and every level of interaction. Each and every level of responses may then lead to different connotations of product meanings; and therefore, studies that are founded on these theories should cover multiple stands of the continuum scale and hold interactionist view.

Concepts of product meanings

There are diverse approaches on the concept and the definition of “meaning”. According to Osgood et al. (1957), meaning may refer to relationship between signs and situations in sociological disciplines, or it may indicate relationships between different signs or significates in linguistic. Crozier (1994) defines meaning as mental organizations of schemas, where schemas are “*coherent units of structured representations of environmental regularities*”. Considering “product meanings” there is no clear concept or universally accepted definition.

The concept of meaning hold by the Affordance Theory generally refers to functional and actionable qualities of products (You & Chen, 2003). In this case meaning is the information that product contains and expresses to its users and environment. Similarly, according to Norman (1990), meaning is the intuition that a product form expresses its function and use. Heft (2003) describes, “*What is perceived through the pick up of information is the affordance of the environment... A surface that is positioned approximately at knee-height relative to a particular person’s leg length is perceived to be sit-on-able; it affords sitting on*”.

Product meanings might also be generated through sensorial experiences. Dagman et al. (2010) proposes “haptic product properties” which is a list of nouns based on studies of Heller and Schiff (1991) and Klatzky and Lederman (2012). Cutting and Vishton (1995) indicate that proximity to a product has an effect on detection of cues and information –meaning-. Correspondingly, Heller (1982) and Schifferstein (2006) propose that involvement sense types depends on the information seeking from the product. Thus, Xenakis and Arnellos (2013) advocate when the user realizes a product at first an aesthetic judgment is performed through vision; then haptic interaction occurs when touched; and at last evaluation of affordances and semantics are made. In this case, each phase may reveal meanings accordingly.

Csikszentmihalyi and Eugene (1981) categorizes meanings in two main groups: person and non-person. There are four sub-groups under person type meanings: self, immediate family, kin and non-family; and there are two sub-categories under non-person meanings: past and present/future related meanings. The past related meanings include those which emerged from memories and associations whereas present/future refers to meanings that are revealed from experiences, intrinsic qualities, style, utilitarian features and personal values. Kujala and Nurkka (2012) mentions three categories of meanings. Personalized meanings includes terms such as motivator, supporter; utility meanings are related to

usability of the product; and tool meanings refer to technical features of the product. Schifferstein (2010) proposes multiple layers of product meanings. The foundation layer comprises affordances and physical qualities of the product which establishes an identity and potential use. The second layer includes meanings generated by symbolic associations. At this level branding, values of the producer, and the context drives meanings. At the highest level, cultural values shape the meaning of the product. This approach resembles Krippendorff’s (1989) contextual descriptions (operational-context, socio-linguistic context, context of genesis and ecological context) and Monö’s (1997) semantic functions of products (describe, express, exhort, identify). In addition, Krippendorff (2006) offers a linguistic classification of meanings in five categories: objective and measurable qualities such as weight or color; interface qualities are the ones that help product to be reliable and used easily; evaluative and aesthetic qualities can be elegance and harmony; meanings refer to social status and positions such as universality or modernity; and emotional qualities are the terms such as satisfying and fun. Furthermore, product meanings might be reflection of personality of users. Many studies illustrate that preference of a product is associated with a match between personality of the users –self– and the identity or the brand value of the product (Belk, 1988; Malhotra, 1988). Personality terms then also appears as product meanings.

There is no clear differentiation between product emotions and product meanings in the literature. According to Desmet and Hekkert (2007) product emotions and meaning may not be separable. A comprehensive study by Desmet (2012) introduces a general typology of positive product emotions. These are sets of meanings revealed by users during their interaction with products. Desmet (2012) suggest that there are six sources of positive product emotions: object refers to emotions elicited by physical qualities of products; meanings indicates associations that users can make with the products; interaction are the emotion that are elicited during the usage of the product; activity is the emotional experiences that product facilitates; self is the emotions that are experienced in response to user’s self-being; and last, other types includes emotions where a product becomes a medium for inter-personal relationships.

Discussions

Current study presents a brief introduction to theoretical perspectives, and it explores their stand on the concept and definition of product meaning. At first, a sharp distinction between the matters of world (objectivist or bottom-up) and the mind (subjectivist or top-down) are presented. A continuum scale that gradually bridges the distinction is introduced. An interactionist approach, which advocates an overlap between matters of the world and mind, is addressed. Subsequently, major theories (Affordance Theory, Product Semantics and Product Emotions) in the field of perception and design is introduced and their theoretical stands are discussed. Due to their stands on the source of knowledge, Affordance Theory is organized under bottom-up approaches, Product

Figure 1. Classification of product meanings and associated theoretical perspectives.

Semantics are placed at the intersection between bottom-up and top-down approaches and Product Emotions are found under top-down approaches (see Figure 1 first row). Afterwards, concepts of product meanings for each aforementioned theory, are introduced and complementary concepts of meaning are discovered. Descriptions and definitions of concepts of product meanings is used to classify product meanings according to theoretical perspectives (see Figure 1 second row).

Product meanings that are revealed by or for affordances, functionality or utilitarian features is considered as level one meanings (see Figure 1 second row, first column). Level one meanings are fundamental and structure-related. They are associated with information that product contains that give them their high level categorical names (if sit-on-able then it is a chair like object). Some meanings that are resulted in sensorial experiences can also be considered level one meanings. Studies interested in these category of meanings may benefit from bottom-up approaches. Level one meanings may reveal at Norman's visceral level, or as Cupchik's

sensorial, Baxter's intrinsic response. Level one meanings may overlap with level two meanings that are found more related to usability and experiences gained at first sight (see Figure 1 second row, second column). Level two meanings refer how well the product informs the user about itself and its functions in certain context. This class of meanings are solution specific and can be related to style (modern office chair). A product should achieve to have level one meaning to gain level two meanings. At this level, meanings may be resulted at Norman's behavioral level, or Cupchik's cognitive, Baxter's semantic response. An interactionist stand may help studies interested in level two studies. Meanings at level three may be the result of prolonged interactions (see Figure 1 second row, third column). The user is most likely to allocate sensorial mechanisms, find the product attractive (appearance), has long exposure of use, and then consider to remember (memorable) the product in order to assign level three meanings to the product. Level three meanings may also be revealed spontaneously when there is a match between the self-image or values of the user and the product. Level three meanings may refer to cultural values or social

status. Furthermore, this category of meanings can be assigned to products due to a key memory of another person or an event. Norman's reflective level, Cupchik's personal, or Baxter's symbolic responses can evoke level three meanings. Bottom-up approaches may be beneficial to understand reasoning behind level three meanings.

To illustrate, a product may trigger sensorial mechanisms and the collected information becomes sources of meanings at first sight. When the experience is extensively gained the surface might be found "comfortable". Thus, the meaning evolves and becomes more definitive about the surface and the experience gained. At the sensorial processing, the surface may be detected as "soft" and "rounded" that is maybe why it feels comfortable. If the overall or final experience is satisfactory and fun, then the surface maybe is "pleasurable" and "liked". Eventually, the surface is sit-on-able, soft, comfortable and fun. If the surface is formed surprisingly strange and unique then it maybe is elegant. In this illustration, several theories have potential applications explaining meaning attribution processes. The illustration is initiated with an affordance. The surface is at the knee level, flat and it affords sitting on and meanings revealed are at level one. Nonetheless, cues on the surface (soft and rounded) suggest that it is potentially comfortable. The user most likely had experienced the same surface qualities before and recalls prior experience. Meanings resulted in this interaction may be at level two. When the surface is used, the experience is found pleasurable since it matches with expectations. At this point, a comparison and appraising occurs. The surface is liked and found fun to sit. Furthermore, when all accumulates, and the surface form is found unique or it matches with self-image of the user, then the surface might be found as "loved" or "elegant" for the particular user. Thus, these meanings may be at level three in which phenomenology might account for an explanation.

Current study is an early attempt to classify product meanings according to theoretical perspectives. A broad classification of product meanings has benefits two benefits. First, it reduces complex nature of the topic and may help increasing our knowledge on the topic. Second, proposed classification illustrates the relationship between product meanings and associated theoretical perspectives which may guide methodological strategies. Although product meanings are previously itemized by many researchers (Dagman et al., 2010; P. Desmet, 2012; Karana & Hekkert, 2010; Karana, Weelderen, & Woerden, 2007; Krippendorff, 2006) and roughly categorized in this paper, further studies are needed for more sensitive identification and precise classification.

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Towards a framework for analysing playful interventions - Lessons from a pink sandbox full of dice

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Introduction

The role of play has been gaining importance in modern society; the rising commercial successes of game and toy industries in the past decades are strong indications of it. As this has most notably taken place during recent decades, the colloquial meaning of 'play' is still often associated with something trivial and non-important. Play is what one engages in within their leisure time and out of the context of serious, work, or meaningful. In 1970, play theorist Brian Sutton-Smith wrote about the need to stop framing play only as activity of children, as "anything that children did, was regarded as not important, and as play." (Sutton-Smith, 1970).

Even though playfulness is often associated with children, there is a tradition of thought that points out how beneficial fun and play can be for adults. In her review of research into this area, Jacqueline Miller (1996) reported that humor at work can relieve stress, improve interpersonal skills, and foster creativity and rapid learning, among other things. Hunter, Jemielniak & Postula (2010) examined how the roles of play and work were tightly interwoven in knowledge-intensive work such as programming. The play activities were

Abstract In this article, a playful intervention called "There Are No Rules" (TANR) is analyzed on three levels: interactions, play behaviors, and play episodes. In the course of five months, students and staff of University of Tampere engaged with an art installation placed in OASIS, a group work area that also functions as a living lab. The experiment period was recorded on video and photographed by the users and the research team. Combined analysis of the video data and photography data exposed a rich and successful playful intervention, positioning TANR as the centerpiece of a playful office and campus environment. The analysis is further cultivated as a framework for future analysis of similar experiments.

Keywords *Dice, Play, Participatory installation, Design research, Interactive experiment*

important for pacing work activities, building work identity, socialization, and creativity.

In this article, a playful art installation called "There Are No Rules" (TANR) is analyzed as a playful intervention, and a framework for analyzing future playful installations is proposed. We are interested in examining installations on three different levels: on the level of basic interactions that the users of the artefact engage in, on the level of play behaviors, and on the level of distinct play episodes that emerge from the interventions. These three levels of the framework provide points of view for analyzing and comparing affordances and contexts of playful interventions.

There Are No Rules (TANR) – A playful art installation

There Are No Rules (Heljakka, 2011) is a pink wooden sandbox-type construct, 1.3 meters to a side. The box is filled with approximately 10,000 small six-sided dice that have colorful dots on their sides (Figure 1). Essentially, the installation affords the same type of play as a regular sandbox: free manipulation and arrangement of the contents, albeit with far larger building blocks.

Figure 1. *There Are No Rules (TANR)* and the artist Kati Heljakka in OASIS.

The origins of this sandbox-type installation were rooted in the idea of complete freedom to play in the box as one pleases. After having exhibited this participatory installation at several exhibitions, it soon occurred to the creator that playing itself is a rule-making process (Unt, 2012). Adults interacting with the unexpected research instrument – the bubblegum pink sandbox – used the artwork in ways similar to how one would use a construction toy such as building blocks, whereas children tended to use it as a platform for a rougher type of play, e.g. paralleling play inside a ball pit. For adults, it was typical to build a structure and leave it standing. Children, again, clearly expressed more interest in exploring the physical affordances of the dice – and their own bodies (Heljakka, 2014).

OASIS

TANR was set up as a research instrument in OASIS (Figure 2), a social learning space at the University of Tampere. OASIS is an informal group work space on a university campus, and it is open to all students, staff members, and visitors. The central design tenets of OASIS dictate that the space should be open, social, playful, shared, and informal, and that it should allow opportunistic use (Kultima et al., 2014). OASIS also functions as a Living Lab environment, with four cameras recording its usage for research purposes, and it has been used as a test bed for several experiments, including the Mur Mur seats (see Nummenmaa et al., 2015). The camera data is also used in a longitudinal study that focuses on the effects that playful interventions and furniture reconfigurations have on how OASIS is used.

Related work on playful interventions

Tieben et al. (2014a) discuss strategies for playful persuasion in public places. They present ten design cases of playful installations with the design goal of encouraging teenagers in high school to increase participation in physical activities. The authors derive three design values from their experiences of designing and evaluating the installations: elicit and seduce; emergent play; and resonate with values, emotions and activities. These design values can also be seen in operation in TANR. The installation is a “seducing” invitation to play because of the inherent play affordances of the dice and the low threshold of starting an interaction. Emergent play is seen in how interactions with the installation itself produce physical and social play behaviors, often in unexpected ways. Emergent play is also open-ended, where the players create their own rules, meanings, and interpretations, thus allowing for many different play styles and sustained motivation for play (Tieben et al., 2014b). By allowing many different ways of approaching and encountering the installation, TANR is by its very nature a good fit for emergent play. Lastly, the installation should resonate with the values, emotions, and activities of the target group and the target environment. In the OASIS case, TANR was installed in an informal group work space that explicitly promotes the values of being open, social, and playful.

Similarly to the evaluation strategy used in TANR, Tieben et al. (2014b) emphasize the importance of evaluating the playful installations in situ, for prolonged periods of time, and with large groups of

Figure 2. OASIS space.

people. Otherwise it is not possible to understand properly how the installation really suits the environment's day-to-day activities and what kinds of interactions and play behaviors emerge over time. Using extensive video data allowed us to include even brief interactions in our analysis, while photos and tweets allowed the analysis of emerging play behaviors and play episodes, and overall observations supported the analysis phase.

Data and method

The data for this study was collected from two sources: video footage and photographs. In addition, the research team occasionally observed the users using TANR in person. In OASIS, video data is continuously recorded using four cameras which together capture a complete view of the space. Two of the cameras were used in observing user interactions with the installation, while footage from the other two cameras was used for recording contextual data as necessary. Two deep analysis periods of videos, totaling 14 days, were selected for examination and analysis of user interactions with the installation.

The photograph data comprises 102 pictures in total and is taken from two specific sources. During the study period, users of OASIS and research team members shared pictures of interactions with TANR on social media. These pictures were tracked on Twitter and Instagram using the established OASIS hashtag #oasisutafi. The pictures were archived, and information on who shared the picture and the time and platform of sharing was recorded. The textual descriptions posted with the pictures were also

retained. In addition to the pictures shared on social media, the research team also took pictures during the study period when an interesting situation, or the traces of an interesting situation, were identified.

The identity of the users of TANR was not tracked, but the general population of the OASIS space is a combination of university students, staff, and visitors. OASIS attracts a notable number of international students and visitors due to the default language of the space being English. The typical user of OASIS is a 20+ male or female student of information sciences.

In the spirit of Grounded Theory (Charmaz, 2006) the experiment data was analyzed iteratively on three different levels: on the level of interactions, play behaviors, and play episodes. The interactions were analyzed by using the video data, whereas play behaviors and play episodes were identified via photographs. The categories of codes were formed iteratively by several researchers. Once they had been identified from the pictures, the play episodes were analyzed further using the video data. In coding the data, the qualitative data tool Atlas.ti was used together with more traditional tools, such as spreadsheets. The details for the analysis of each level is presented in the *Findings* section and further elaborated into a framework in the *Framework for analyzing playful interventions* section.

Findings

This chapter presents the findings from three distinct levels of analysis: **interactions**, play behaviors, and play episodes. Constructed through observing ongoing

user activity, interactions are the fundamental meaningful ways in which users engaged with the installation, and eleven categories of them were identified: adding, removing, building, breaking, modifying, fiddling, examining, throwing, body interaction, scooping, and taking pictures. Using a different temporal and analytical perspective, wider patterns of play and playfulness, called play behaviors, were observed. Eight categories of **play behaviors** were identified and named, including color play, constructing, environment play, physical play, object play, narrative play, transgressive play, and wordplay. Finally, altogether 42 **play episodes**, or periods of playful user activity and behavior, were identified from the data of photographs. Seven of them were further analyzed using the video data and are highlighted in this article: Floor Face, Kenny Escaping, Thin Towers, Peace, Stripes, Photoshoot, and Red and Blue Ghost.

Interactions

Using the video footage from OASIS, user interactions with the installation were observed. Two observation periods were chosen: the first starting when the installation was first set up in order to explore initial user reactions to the installation, and the second period starting two months later when the installation had become an established feature of the space. For the purposes of the analysis presented in this paper, both periods were examined exploratively and not directly compared with each other. A researcher viewed footage from the two observation periods, taking notes and iteratively defining the interaction categories. The analysis was informed by simultaneous exploration of play behaviors and play cases (described later), which led to revisiting and refining some of the categories.

The interactions were recorded within user sessions. A session was defined to start when a user began an interaction and to end when they left the installation and did not return to resume the interaction momentarily. As such, the duration of the observed user sessions ranged from a few seconds to 2 hours, and they could contain multiple types of interactions: for example, a session might begin as examining a previous user's work, continue as modifying it, and conclude with building something new. Based on the data, the interactions were divided into 11 different categories

- adding: *adding items to the dice box*
- removing: *taking items or dice out of the dice box*
- building: *constructing a specific artifact out of the dice by rearranging or placing the dice one by one*
- breaking: *dismantling a previously built artifact completely or partially*
- modifying: *making changes or additions to a previously built artifact*
- fiddling: *activity that is noncommittal in nature and lacks a definite goal or purpose; playing around with the dice; can be secondary to some other simultaneous activity (e.g. done while talking to someone)*
- examining: *curious and/or focused examination of the dice box contents without physically touching them*

- throwing: *picking up dice from the box and throwing or tossing them back in*
- body interaction: *interacting with the dice box using the whole body, for example by standing, sitting, lying, or walking on the dice*
- scooping: *moving large amounts of dice by scooping them or digging to expose the floor under the dice*
- taking pictures: *photographing the installation, its contents, or users interacting with it*

During the first period, 74 user sessions were observed, and during the second period, 24 sessions were observed. These 98 user sessions involved a total of 129 users and 129 interactions:

Table 1. The occurrences of the interactions on the examined data slice.

Interaction	Occurrences
Fiddling	55
Modifying	27
Building	21
Breaking	5
Throwing	4
Examining	4
Adding	3
Removing	3
Body interaction	3
Scooping	2
Taking pictures	2

By analyzing the footage from two video cameras over two observation periods, we were able to track user interactions with the installation and to divide them into 11 distinct categories. Seven of the interaction types stem from the primary affordances of the installation, focusing around manipulating the dice in different ways. Other interactions used external objects or tools, such as toys that were added to the installation or cameras used for taking pictures, or involve either more extensive physical contact with the installation, such as body interaction, or none at all, such as examining the installation. In the end, the analysis portrays fiddling as TANR's factual main interaction.

In order to achieve a broader understanding of the effects of the interactive installation and phenomena surrounding it, user activities and their results were also approached from the perspective of playfulness and using a different data set, leading to an analysis of play behaviors.

Play behaviors

The data consisted of 102 pictures, 66 of which were taken by the research team, while the rest of the pictures were collected from social media. The pictures were analyzed by first identifying whether they portrayed playing – either traces of earlier play or actual ongoing play. The captions of the shared social media pictures were included in the analysis. 76 of the

images included some traces of play behaviors. These pictures were then analyzed in more detail to categorize different play behaviors.

Although our sample was relatively small, the play behaviors were surprisingly versatile in terms of physicality, expression, and using other objects. Based on the photograph and social media data, we were able to identify at least eight categories, including color play, constructing, environment play, physical play, object play, narrative play, transgressive play and wordplay. Although a comprehensive list of play behaviors was identified, it should be noted that this list is most likely not exhaustive, and some behaviors were left unfound.

Color play includes forming pixel art, text, and other formations by using the colors of the dice. Constructing means stacking dice to form structures, such as pyramids and towers. Environment play takes advantage of the surroundings of the box, namely its borders and the floor under the dice. Physical play is found from the pictures that include active playing around and inside the box, such as sitting among the dice and throwing the dice in the air. Object play uses other objects, such as toys, inside or on the sides of the dice box. In narrative play, users had created stories or scenarios, such as a doll with the dice cleared around it, making it seem like the doll had made a snow angel. Transgressive play is only recorded once in a photo that included a die that had a heart drawn on it. Wordplay is written jokes or witty remarks, typically found as a description of the picture shared on social media. This was the only play behavior found in the actual social media shares, not the actual photos, but not exclusively, as one wordplay behavior written with the dice was also identified.

The discovered play behavior categories were linked to play episodes identified from the pictures (see Table 2). Many play episodes continued in several different pictures, and some episodes included several different play behavior types. For instance, dolls set on the side of the box were identified as both object and environment play. Two categories of play behavior were dominant in TANR: color play and constructing. In the following chapter, the play episodes are examined in detail to further understanding of TANR as a playful installation.

Table 2. The occurrences of play behaviors in connection to play episodes.

Play behavior	Episodes connected	Number of codes
Constructing	19	36
Environment play	14	23
Color play	12	39
Object play	12	19
Wordplay	7	10
Physical play	5	19
Narrative play	3	3
Transgressive play	1	1

Play episodes

As the dice-filled sandbox afforded manipulation of the play pieces, we observed a wide variety of creative and playful activities that often extended into synchronous or asynchronous social episodes. These activities left a mark on the box and were also often photographed by the users. Such manifestations of play as different constructions and constellations were identified from the photograph data by tagging the photos collaboratively using Atlas.ti. A total of 42 smaller play episodes were identified, and selected episodes were analyzed in more detail. This analysis used the video data to determine how the episodes evolved, how many players were involved, and the length of the episodes (see Table 3). The following eight play episodes highlighted from the data represent the variety of play emerging from the experiments. The episodes were named as: Floor Face, Kenny Escaping, Thin Towers, Peace, Stripes, Photoshoot, and Red and Blue Ghost (Figure 3).

In the *Floor Face* episode, a group of six people are standing next to the dice box, deep in conversation. One of them sits on the edge of the box, clears out a small circular area to expose the floor beneath the dice, and then moves to the other side of the box and clears out another similar area. Another person then joins in and clears a linear area, creating a semblance of a face in the box. The first person then modifies the ‘mouth’ to show a smile. Both of them add dice to the circular openings to emphasize their eye-like appearance. Several other people make small modifications to the face, add toys to the box, and take pictures.

In the *Kenny Escaping* episode, one person builds a set of stairs reaching to the edge of the box in about 10 minutes, at one point pausing to talk with two people who have approached the dice box and are observing what is being built. The person then leaves OASIS and comes back with a Kenny figurine (from the South Park animated series), places it on the edge of the dice box next to the stairs, and takes more pictures. The person then leaves the stairs and the figurine in place and remains in OASIS.

In the *Thin Towers* episode, one person starts building a construction, and after a little while, two other people join in, one first and the other a minute or so later. They continue for around 20 minutes, constructing various buildings out of the dice. One person takes off their shoes and sits in the box. Two of the people are co-operating (they are working on the same side of the box and are very close to each other), but the third person appears to be working on their own.

In the *Peace* episode, there is no footage of the initial construction and modifications to the artefact from the first 3 days due to technical difficulties. However, its initial stages were observable from social media pictures, and several interesting interactions could be identified from the later video footage. On the third day of the play episode, a group of five people enters OASIS and examines the dice box for a while. One of them starts modifying the artefact, and 3 others join

1. Floor Face
2. Kenny Escaping
3. Thin Towers
4. Peace
5. Stripes
6. Photoshoot
7. Red and Blue Ghost

Figure 3. Selected TANR play episodes. From left to right: Floor Face, Kenny Escaping, Thin Towers, Peace, Stripes, Photoshoot, and Red and Blue Ghost.

in soon. One additional person joins in later. They add hearts and colored dice to the artefact. The activity lasts approximately 10 minutes. Four days later, on Monday, a single person comes into OASIS, examines the artefact in the dice box for a while, changes the textual component of the artefact, and leaves. The activity lasts approximately 10 minutes. Couple of hours later on the same day a single person picks up a few dice from the box, adds them to the artefact, and leaves. The activity lasts for approximately 20 seconds. On Tuesday one person starts to modify the artefact. Two other people join in very briefly. The activity lasts for less than two minutes. Later on the same day, a person starts to wipe the artefact and build something new. Overall, the Peace episode endured for ten days, constantly evolving into something different.

In the *Stripes* episode, three people stand around the dice box and after a while, two of them start arranging the dice. The third person stays in the sidelines for a minute, helping out a little bit, then joins in on the activity. Patterns of colored stripes start to emerge. After finishing rearranging the entire top layer of dice, they take pictures of the result, stay for a little while, and then leave OASIS. The entire endeavor took about 2 hours and 15 minutes.

In the *Photoshoot* episode, two people enter OASIS, and one of them sets up camera equipment near the dice box. The other person sits in the dice box, and they take photos for a while.

In the *Red and Blue Ghost* episode, a single person starts to clear out the artefact in the center of the dice box on Thursday, to create an even and level surface of white dice, and to gather a set of dice with a red side. This phase of the activity continues for about 1 hour. The first person starts to construct a rendering of a Pacman ghost from the red dice previously set aside. The second person pulls out their phones and appears to take pictures. This phase of the activity lasts for about half an hour. On Friday, one person examines the artefact, takes pictures of it, and then rearranges some of the dice to expand the white 'floor' on which

the Pacman ghost is. On Monday, two people come into OASIS and one of them heads straight for the dice box, puts one foot on the white 'floor', and messes up the dice, avoiding destroying the Pacman ghost, while the other observes. On Wednesday, one person starts building another artefact next to the red Pacman ghost. After finishing what turns out to be a blue Pacman ghost right next to the red one, the builder takes a picture of the dice box and leaves OASIS.

The affordances of the dice and the busy social space enabled asynchronous messaging lasting as long as ten days as an evolving play episode. The box invited people to play in different social constellations: some played alone, yet continuing or contributing to someone else's previous work, some came together as a group and started anew, while some were engaging as a more passive bystander or in autotelic play. Altogether, the play episodes were diverse and there were relatively many of them portraying TANR as a rich platform for play.

These three different levels of analysis build an interesting cross-section of a playful artefact as an intervention in a social space. The different affordances of the artefact and the space promote certain kinds of play activities: the dice afford

Table 3. The selected play episodes, their durations and the number of the people involved.

Name of the episode	Duration of the episode	Number of the people involved
Floor Face	10 min.	6
Kenny Escaping	15 min.	3
Thin Towers	25 min.	3
Peace	10 days	5, 1, 1, 3, 1, 2, 1 (several occasions, in order)
Stripes	2 h 15 min.	3
Photoshoot	5 min.	2
Red and Blue Ghost	7 days	2, 1, 2, 1, 2 (several occasions, in order)

building and the dots on the dice color play, the public space hindered transgressive play and created social chains of asynchronous play, and the box frames the area of play, providing people a safe distance for passive engagement as well as different levels for active engagements. The affordance of permanence of the dice also provided invitations for play as the constructions, object play, and various pixel art creations were evidence of the permission of participation.

Framework for analyzing playful interventions

As the TANR experiment was a successful playful intervention engaging the users in a wide variety of playful interactions and forms of play, future studies of similar artefacts would be beneficial. The three layers identified in the study form an interconnected framework for both design and analysis of similar kinds of playful interventions. The basic atomic interactions in the first layer are determined by the immediate affordances of the different components of the intervention. In the case of TANR, the huge number of dice and the physical dimensions and the location of the sandbox give rise to interaction categories of spatial configuration (building, breaking, and modifying), external (adding, removing, and body interaction), fiddling (fiddling, scooping, and throwing), and observation (examining and taking pictures).

The interplay of these basic interactions together with an aim external to the affordances gives rise to the longer term play behaviors identified in the study. In other words, the analysis level of play behavior takes into account what the players try to achieve within the interaction. For example, the play behavior category constructing is simply a sequence of spatial configuration interactions aiming at more vertical constructions while in color play the aim is to use the spatial configuration to create recognizable iconic or symbolic representations.

The emergence of play episodes is dependent not only on the physical characteristics of the intervention and its immediate surroundings but also on the social dynamics of the environment. In this case, OASIS as an informal group work space on a university campus made the play episodes fluid both over time and in player composition. In synchronous play the players involved in the episode join and leave the interaction at the same time, as exemplified in the Photoshoot episode. TANR also supports asynchronous play even for periods of several days as players are not necessary for maintaining the play state, in this case the physical configuration of the dice in the sandbox. In asynchronous play the players can join and leave the episode as they wish, and in many cases there were no active players at all for long periods of time. Because of its size, TANR also support parallel play where even though the players are playing in the same place at the same time, they are not trying to influence each other's behavior, as was exemplified in the Thin Towers episode.

This framework provides a high-level guide for the analysis of the interactions that can happen in playful interventions. The framework, of course, is not exhaustive and further analyses and design of interventions will provide a more elaborate and effective categorization.

Discussion and future work

The TANR experiment proved to be a rich source for material in creating an initial framework for analyzing playful interventions. The decision to take a three-level approach to the analysis, and to have two distinct data sources, with the added data collected through the in-person observations of the researchers, was effective in shining light into various aspects of TANR.

Due to the affordance for color play and the permanence of the dice, TANR could be interpreted as a type of platform for social graffiti. On a number of studies (Stocker, Dutcher, Hargrove & Cook, 1972; Islam, 2010; Trahan, 2011) analyzing graffiti and the culture surrounding them, humor or playfulness have been found out being amongst the top thematic categories. Looking at the way people interacted with TANR, it also has similarities to graffiti. According to Halsey (2006) for the graffiti artist an unpainted wall is just a blank canvas, an invitation to play. In a similar way a box full of colorful dice can be seen as a canvas with an invitation to play. However, the tactile nature of the dice also afforded notable amount of physical fiddling.

A kind of a sub-set for graffiti, toilet writings, or latrinalia, are an interesting case of public, yet at the same time private playful behavior. As the restroom stall offers almost complete anonymity to graffitiists, contents of latrinalia are usually something people would not write publicly. Still at the same time they are used to convey messages to other toilet users, thus creating a temporal bond between the writer and the others. (Young, 2009.) Interestingly, in the experiment of TANR, only one case of transgressive play was recorded. Even though the art installation was named as something without rules, the activity was somewhat conventional possibly due to the all-encompassing public nature of the installation. Further, the play activities extending over several days resembled the temporal bond noted in the latrinalia. Earlier studies of into play as communication have revealed the generally ambiguous character of playful communication (Mäyrä, 2012).

There is a rising interest in public playful interventions. These interventions include interactive art installations, such as Martin Creed's art piece featuring a room half-full of balloons (Now. Here. This., 2014), and publicity stunts, such as Volkswagen's Piano Stairs (Volkswagen, 2009) or Pearlfisher's pool filled with white ball pit balls (Hooton, 2015). They can also be a result of student research work, as in StreetPong, a game to play while waiting the traffic lights to turn green (Hutchings, 2012). A comparison of different playful installations and their factual interactions could improve our understanding of the design of playful interventions. As a future work, we aim to examine an artefact inspired by Pearlfisher's

experiment – a bathing barrel filled with ball pit balls – in the same context as TANR to find out how much of the similarities and differences among these two cases are formed in terms of interaction, play behaviors, and play episodes.

Conclusions

In this article, a playful intervention (TANR) was analyzed on three different levels – interactions, play behaviors, and play episodes. The three-level analysis proved fruitful, as it provided deeper understanding of the characteristics of the intervention. Based on this analysis, a framework was created to work as a high-level guide for the analysis of playful interactions in playful interventions. The framework, although not yet exhaustive, can be used for future analysis of playful interventions and installations in order to compare different artefacts and their modalities and further develop the framework. The future analysis can be compared to the results of the analysis of TANR, which revealed an artifact where the main interaction was noncommittal fiddling, with various color play and constructing play behaviors resulting in a diverse set of social play episodes.

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Towards a cellulose-based society: Demonstrating the feasibility of new bio-based material concepts and products

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Abstract In moving towards a cellulose-based society, interdisciplinary effort is required as it is at this interface that new ideas are found and can grow. New bio-based materials will play a key role but getting them into the marketplace is not always straightforward. Many options are available both for sourcing and for producing composite materials from wood-based cellulose and poly-lactic acid (PLA). Depending on how the material is processed, a multitude of properties can be generated. The main goal with this work was to attempt to reduce the research-to-market gap. This was done by testing a new way of working together where we bundled innovation-oriented projects and research-oriented projects around the theme of material experience. We then systematically worked with material demonstrators. In this article, we exemplify the results by focusing on one research-oriented project that did not at the outset have a market context and on one innovation-oriented project with clear market requirements. In addition to introducing a new concept in bundling research-oriented and innovation-oriented projects, this paper contributes several practical examples of what material demonstrators can do. We also present an application and analysis of Moultrie's extended Science-Technology-Application-Market (STAM) model to analyze the material demonstrators and design phases of the bundled projects. We modified the proposed classification with different types of material demonstrators according to how close they are to an actual product segment. Designers and scientists worked together but with different emphasis in each phase.

Keywords *Bio-based materials, Demonstrators, Design, Experience, STAM model*

Introduction

As science and technology continue to move forward towards renewable and more environmentally friendly materials and processes, interdisciplinary effort is required in order to achieve groundbreaking research in material and product development (Golembiewski et.al. 2015) 'The bio-based economy can and should be to the 21st century what the fossil-based economy was to the 20th century' according to Hardy (Hardy 2002, p.11). This statement emphasizes not only the relevance of the bio economy for both academia and industry but the need for research efforts to join different disciplines. Bio-based materials are central to implementing a bio-based economy. Cellulose is the most abundant organic polymer on earth (Klemm et.al. 2005) and one of the most promising renewable source materials to replace commodity plastics is Polylactic acid (PLA).

PLA is a biodegradable plastic made from starch that combined with wood pulp creates a material that acquires new properties when heated. PLA fibers and wood pulp fibers are commingled to produce a generic

paper multi-material, where distinctively different properties can be enhanced depending on the processing and converting stages. The ratio of pulp to PLA can be varied and the material can be produced on a full-scale pilot paper machine or extruded, hot pressed or injection molded. Different applications can be created, e.g. clothing applications by creping and pleating the material or boards by using hot pressing (Granberg et al., 2015).

The structure in the material will define the material properties. Relevant material properties can be tailored by designing the components (e.g. designing the fibre), the composition of components (e.g. component blends, fibre properties and orientations etc.) and the product property requirements. Lindström (Lindström et.al. 2014) calls this approach hierarchic design and points out the importance of interdisciplinary translation and cooperation between material scientists and designers. In this model, the component design level is dominated by scientists and influenced by the designer, while the product design stage is mostly dominated by designers but still with

Figure 1. Pulp-PLA composite produced on paper machine and creped (left), injection molded (middle), and 3D printed (right).

the input of scientists. The steps between these see designers and scientists working together, iterating between the different possible realisations of each step and narrowing in on the way forward.

Introducing new materials, especially if they have new properties, can be a lengthy process. There is a need for better understanding how to systematically explore new bio-based materials. This type of exploration usually entails some form of material swatches, demonstrators and even early product-level prototyping which can be used to communicate about the material. This article describes some methods for exploring new materials and then classifying the demonstrators to better understand how to decrease the research-to-market gap.

Methods

The materials in focus were made from cellulose and PLA. Some examples are shown in Figure 1. They exemplify the span of how different materials made from these components can be. They also show the different processing methods that are possible.

Meaning of materials

One of the keys to the commercial success of new bio-plastic materials is that they be introduced with unique aesthetic properties emphasizing that they are different to the ones currently on the marketplace (Karana, 2012; Karana et.al. 2015). New forest-based renewable composites should thus not only fulfil technical requirements, they should also appeal to users' senses and render an intended meaning to products. Material experience combines the ways in which we perceive a material via our senses and through associations with its physical properties (Jonsson et.al. 2008; Karana, 2012; Karana et.al. 2009; Lindberg et.al. 2013). Many factors affect the way a material is perceived: how it is processed, the product it is embodied in, when it is used, and the background of the user, i.e. culture, gender, previous experiences etc. (Karana et.al. 2010).

TechMark Arena

In order to explore new ways to communicate the principles of materials science to a non-scientific audience and bridge the research-to-market gap for new bio-based materials, the TechMark Arena was launched. It is structured as a program where research-oriented master's projects are bundled and

run in teams with innovation-oriented master's projects (Béland et.al. 2015). The eight students were from three different universities and were supervised by a team of five researchers. By combining material scientists with students from different disciplines, a new way to test the pathway of new material concepts from the lab to the marketplace was explored. Instead of running individual master's projects on specific questions, several master's students were coordinated to address a common theme from different perspectives. For the 2015 program the theme was new bio-based materials related to material experience and market potential. The projects included in 2015 are briefly presented here.

1. Stimuli-responsive degradation of a textile-like pulp/PLA material modified by polyelectrolyte assembly. (Research-oriented project)

The constantly new and changing fashion industry combined with sales and cheap garments are highly influencing factors dominating the fast quantitative usage of apparel in the Western world. Carried out by chemistry student Tove Kristensen, from KTH Royal Institute of Technology (Kristensen, 2015), the project evaluated an alternative to developing clothes that will last forever. Instead, manufacturing biocomposite fabrics on a paper machine and incorporating a stimuli-induced degradation process creates a "fast fashion" alternative. Garments are used for 1-5 days and then degrade when composted. The project was designed as a pre-study for a broader project which attempts to examine the vision of a deliberate degradation process of textile-like PLA/wood fibre material triggered by the body during use.

2. Material Identity Crisis: Tailoring the properties of a material showing its potential through a demonstrator. (Research-oriented project)

The title Material Identity Crisis was chosen as it brings together the two crucial parts of the project. The fact that the material is a new bio-based material creates a material identity crisis in itself. Textile-like PLA-paper does not necessarily belong to any of the traditional groups of materials. Another perspective on a material identity crisis is to stress a material's properties for it to be perceived in different ways. Carried out by product development and design students Anna Nilsson and Hanna Skoglund from Linköping University (Nilsson & Skoglund, 2015), a material-driven product development process was

used to explore the behaviour of textile-like PLA-paper for a packaging solution.

3. Economics/added-value of bio-based materials from the forest (Research-oriented project)

The aim was to investigate the bio-based added value of bio-based packaging and packaging materials. Economics student Karl Berntsson, SLU, the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, investigated possible competitive advantages of bio-based alternatives, willingness to pay for and the ability to obtain a green price premium for bio-based materials and products. Preliminary results (the thesis is not yet registered) indicate that there is added value linked to bio-based materials and products that is not found in corresponding petroleum-based materials and products.

4. Possibilities and limitations for a bio-based composite to be used as speaker cabinet material (Innovation-oriented project)

A producer of high quality speaker cabinets was looking for alternatives to medium-density fibreboard (MDF), to make production of their cabinets faster, cheaper and more environmentally friendly. Industrial product development student Benoît Coste, KTH Royal Institute of Technology (Coste, 2015) evaluated the possibility offered by bio-composites containing pulp fibres, like more shaping options, faster manufacturing than MDF, possibility to process by injection moulding, and reduced impact on the environment compared to fossil-based plastics. A functional user-centred speaker cabinet prototype was made and its production feasibility investigated.

5. Next Generation of Active Underwear - Implementing Smart Textiles and Technologies (Innovation-oriented project)

Active Underwear is underwear aimed at sports applications. The demand for smart textiles and technologies is predicted to increase but it is not always obvious how to make best use of available solutions. Industrial product development students Elin Cadenius and Kim Gartvall, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, in collaboration with Björn Borg (Cadenius & Gartvall, 2015), developed new innovative and sustainable concepts for doing just this. They also mapped relevant textiles and technologies implementable in sports underwear. The project compared a number of commercially used sportswear textiles with a number of newer textiles made from natural fibres.

6. Bio-based Clothes Covers for a High-end Clothing Brand (Innovation-oriented project)

There is a growing interest in using plastics from renewable resources and other bio-based materials to replace conventional fossil-based plastics. New clothes covers intended for hanging clothes (primarily suits) also needed to be compatible in the current transport chain, be aesthetically appealing, and add value by being used by end-users as a transport bag. Industrial product development student Sebastian de Arteaga, KTH Royal Institute of Technology (de Arteaga, 2015) worked in collaboration with Tiger of Sweden. A large number of suitable bio-based materials were

evaluated. Two concepts were generated for the brand based on commercially available bio-based polyethylene, and a more long-term compostable concept was investigated that used bio-based materials combining PLA, wood-based fibres and nanocellulose.

Technology Readiness Level and STAM

The framework of Technology Readiness Level (TRL) as defined by NASA is increasingly used as a way to categorize technological development and to classify research and innovation, e.g. by the European Commission. Moultrie (Moultrie, 2015) examined the role of demonstrators in scientific activity and classified them according to the Science, Technology, Application, Market (STAM) framework. TRL can be mapped onto STAM but STAM is broader in scope and covers the whole span from scientific discovery to commercialisation. Of interest for analysing our demonstrators is that the STAM framework also contains a proposal of different types of demonstrators aligned with the model. We use Moultrie's extended STAM model that includes Science, Technology, Future Application, Specific Application, and Potential Market as the phases of progression. The purpose of the classification is to help understand the role of demonstrators in the research-to-market process.

Results and discussion

User's sensory perception and appraisal of material/product was a common denominator in 4 of the 6 projects and the studies performed addressed different levels of material perception and meaning. Sensorial properties as well as affective attributes were evaluated to different degrees depending on closeness to the market. Some of the investigated attributes were used within several projects. An overview of the attributes is shown in Table 1. The materials developed in the research-oriented projects were also included in some of the studies of the innovation-oriented projects. This made it possible to compare the new materials with existing materials for specific applications, while conducting studies without context.

The research-oriented projects focused on the development of new materials and how their properties could be explored and communicated. In these projects, the focus was to understand how the material could be formulated and processed to be suitable for different applications and to generate different perceptual responses for the users.

The innovation-oriented projects had a pre-defined market context with the specific issues having been defined by collaborating companies. These projects included investigations of both existing and new materials in the context of specific market applications. The focus was to identify materials that, in addition to possessing the required technical properties, were perceived in ways consistent with the brand and desirable for the applications.

The TechMark Arena 2015 projects were defined with starting points either focused on the potential (new)

uses of new bio-based materials or on specific market segments requiring the investigation and use of new bio-based alternatives to existing materials. All projects, except project 3 that analyzed economics, focused on material development, exploration and application possibilities. The approximate fit of the projects with the different STAM phases is shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Sensorial and affective attributes investigated in four of the projects.

Attributes	TechMark Arena Project			
	2 (Material identity crisis)	4 (Speaker Cabinets)	5 (Smart textiles)	6 (Clothes covers)
Affective				
Luxurious	X			X
Masculine				X
Modern		X		X
Premium				X
Unique	X	X		X
Lively	X			
Natural	X	X		
Fun	X	X		
Expensive	X	X		
Extravagant	X	X		
High quality	X	X	X	
Playful	X			
Serious	X			
Eco-friendly		X		
Furniture-like		X		
Ugly		X		
Minimalistic		X		
Professional		X		
Comfortable			X	
Sporty			X	
Textile-like	X			
Paper-like	X			
Sensorial				
Soft	X		X	
Smooth	X		X	
Matte	X			
Reflective	X			
Cold/cool	X		X	
Elastic	X			
Opaque	X			
Ductile	X			
Strong	X			
Light	X			
Good breathability			X	
Good support			X	
Stays dry			X	

Within the TechMark Arena, material development was carried out both in context, as for the innovation-oriented projects dealing with clothes covers, smart textiles, and speaker cabinets, and without context, as in the research-oriented material identity crisis project. Those projects that started with the market segment already defined led to both proposed solutions for immediate implementation and to solutions that in the longer term could take advantage of new bio-based materials.

In other words, the projects' focus started in the potential market phase and evolved into concepts requiring technology development. Regardless of whether the projects were carried out in context or without; demonstrators were an important part of the process for all projects. The types ranged from abstract demonstrators at laboratory scale showing technical possibilities, to both future and specific application demonstrators for well-defined market segments. When a project started with newly developed materials and the aim was to explore potential avenues for using the material, demonstrators tended to start with the science and technology phases and move towards the market phase.

It is out of scope to present results from all projects. In the next sections, we highlight the results of one research-oriented project that did not at the outset have a market context and one innovation-oriented project with clear market requirements.

Creating a design concept using the MoM tool – research-oriented project case

The project Material Identity Crisis (Nilsson & Skoglund, 2015) revolved around textile-like pulp-PLA paper in combination with creping, heat treatment, and folding in order to control both form freedom and experience properties of a new multilateral. We expand on this case as a research-oriented project.

The expected outcome was a demonstrator that utilises the advantages of textile-like materials and possible conversion techniques. Two different meanings were selected, namely *Luxurious* and *Playful*. Using the Meaning of Material (MoM) Survey

Table 2. TechMark Arena projects that dealt with materials and their approximate fit to the different extended STAM phases.

Project fit with STAM phases*	STAM phases				
	Science	Technology	Future Application	Specific Application	Potential Market
1 (Chemistry)	100%				
2 (Material identity crisis)		70%	20%	10%	
4 (Speaker cabinets)		20%	20%	60%	
5 (Smart textiles)			20%	80%	
6 (Clothes covers)			30%	60%	10%

* Project 3 was not technological in nature and is not included here.

Figure 2. Examples of uploaded images of Luxurious (left) and Playful (right).

proposed by Karana (Karana et al., 2010) 73 respondents gave an example of a material they thought was *Luxurious* (n=36), and one they thought of as *Playful* (n=37). Respondents also uploaded a picture of the material embodied in a product, explained why they thought the material was luxurious or playful and then rated the chosen material on a sensorial scale.

The results showed that materials perceived as *Luxurious* are *smooth, glossy, not elastic and strong*. The uploaded pictures showed materials that can be divided in two groups; soft materials dominated by fabrics (notably silk) and hard materials dominated by metals and minerals. The majority of the pictures featured materials with a smooth finish. Some participants wrote that a rare or unique material is luxurious.

Materials perceived as *Playful* are *soft, smooth, opaque, ductile and light*. The uploaded pictures showed materials in industrially mass produced products with several colours, many embodied in a product that had been manufactured through moulding. The uploaded pictures (Figure 2) show examples of luxurious and playful materials embedded in products.

The Materials Identity Crisis project also produced a number of material demonstrators. These were classified as abstract, conceptual, or “productified” (Béland & Granberg 2015) depending on how close they were to an actual product segment.

Abstract demonstrators were created based on the results of the MoM survey in order to understand the effect of process parameters on material perception (Table 3, rows 1-2). Batches of the textile-like PLA-paper were produced and processed using different dye types and nip pressures. Karana refers to this step as “tinkering with the material” (Karana et.al. 2015). The resulting demonstrators were evaluated on the sensorial scales from the MoM survey with a different (new) group of respondents (n=23). The results showed that the material samples were perceived as opaque, non-reflective, light weight,

tough, matte and ductile. In addition, samples were also compared for the selected meanings, *Luxurious* and *Playful*, by placing them on a 2-dimensional visual analogue scale with orthogonal axes.

Nilsson & Skoglund (2015) then compared how the material demonstrators performed with respect to the desired material properties from the initial MoM-survey. It was found that the desired playful properties could be fulfilled with the textile-like PLA-paper as long as the right samples were chosen. The desired luxurious properties were less fulfilled by the material as is and further conversion could achieve the desired properties. Heat treatment was tried as way of altering both the material properties and the material expression in the desired directions. This work led to the abstract demonstrator depicted on the second row in Table 3.

Based on the results from the MoM-survey design guidelines were established as a starting point for the development of two demonstrators. These included recommendations regarding for example shape, color, patterns and surfaces. Beverage packaging was selected as the application and it was decided that two different demonstrators would be developed, one expressing *Playful* and one expressing *Luxury*.

Conceptual demonstrators were produced to show both potential contexts for use and the different ways the material can be processed and converted. From this, more concrete sketches were made before testing different variations in 2D mock-ups (Table 3, rows 3 and 5). These served as the basis for discussion in a workshop and helped narrow down the possibilities for the visualization stage of the project (Table 3, rows 4 and 6). The conceptual demonstrators played a critical role in invention, serving both to communicate material properties and ideas for potential use as well as inspiring entirely new materials. One invention disclosure came out of the process, followed by an application to patent.

Productified 3D demonstrators were the last to be produced in the project and expressed the two very different attributes of *Luxury* and *Playful* in the

Figure 3. Visualization of the mean scores given to the luxurious (left) and playful (right) champagne packaging concepts. Black lines and dark blue circles show significant results.

context of packaging for a champagne bottle (Table 3, last row). The material is processed and converted to show a possible use within this market segment and a final perception study was performed in order to find out if the intended attributes were being expressed. The study was made through a survey based on the semantic differential method (Krippendorff & Butter 1984). Apart from the attributes *Luxurious* and *Playful*, some complementary adjective pairs of interest were investigated. Twenty-six respondents participated in this study. The luxurious concept was considered to be significantly ($p < 0.5$) serious, unique, extravagant, calm, expensive and high quality (Figure 3, left). There were many positive comments about the design but it was also stated that the perception of the material as exclusive and luxurious was hindered by its tactile properties and the lack of preciseness in the execution of the demonstrator. The playful concept was considered to be significantly ($p < 0.5$) playful, lively, unique, artificial, cheerful, fun, extravagant, cheap and not luxurious (Figure 3, right).

In moving from the Science STAM phase towards the Potential Market STAM phase, the type of material demonstrator changes from abstract, to conceptual to “productified” but not necessarily in a linear fashion. This indicates that RDI demonstrators are iterative in their nature. Identifying the best type of demonstrator to produce requires that it be placed in a relevant context. This helped us in identifying potential market segments for which new materials are needed, either by modifying the materials demonstrators developed within the projects or by developing completely new materials.

Creating a design concept for an innovation-oriented project case

We present here partial results from project 6, Bio-based Clothes Covers for a High-end Clothing Brand. In this project a material experience study was performed as part of the material selection process. The study was made with two different test groups; one group with respondent from the general public (potential consumers) and one test group consisting of staff at the company (designers, purchasers, production coordinators etc.). In total 28 respondents participated in the study.

The participants were asked to evaluate 13 different

samples regarding 5 different attributes (see Table 1). The given context was materials for clothes covers. The material samples were chosen based on their abilities to fulfil the technical requirements for the application and consisted of both opaque and transparent materials, e.g. plastics, plastic films, paper/board and textile-like composite materials. The textile-like Pulp/PLA material investigated in the research-oriented projects was also included among the samples. This gave us the opportunity to explore how this new material performed compared to existing materials within this specific context.

The results showed that a black, shiny, non-elastic polyester fabric performed well for many of the attributes. For the attribute *Luxurious* this material scored high in both groups. This result agrees well with the results from the MoM-survey performed in the Material identity Crisis project which showed that materials perceived as *Luxurious* are smooth, glossy, not elastic and strong. However, the textile-like pulp/PLA sample was ranked the most luxurious, unique and premium by the consumer group. This also agrees with the final perception study performed in the Material identity Crisis project where both concepts were considered as significantly unique. For the plastic materials, the sample that scored highest was a two-sided matte/glossy 170 μm thick polyethylene film. Many respondent stated that stiffer and thicker plastic materials are more luxurious and of higher quality. Several respondents disliked the plastic samples that wrinkled. Opaque plastics were preferred over transparent; several respondents stated that transparent plastic was perceived as cheap, especially if it was hazy. The results were similar for the paper materials, the thicker samples performed better than the thin ones.

When comparing the results between the two test groups some differences could be identified. Some materials that were ranked lower by the company staff were preferred by the consumer group. One reason could be that the company staff had a deeper knowledge of the materials and therefore were more critical. It could also be that they were biased in that they recognized some of the materials. However, none of the groups showed significant opposite results where a sample scored significantly above average for one group but under average for the other.

Table 3. Material demonstrators of the Material Identity Crisis project, approximate fit with the STAM phases, and whether they were mainly the result of the work of the scientists (S), designers (D), or a collaborative effort.

Science	Technology	Future Application	Specific Application	Potential Market	Material Identity Crisis project: Material demonstrators in chronological order
	◆	◆			<p>Abstract demonstrators showing first color swatches of the new material</p> <p>S</p>
	◆	◆			<p>Abstract demonstrators showing color change after heat treatment</p> <p>S</p>
		◆	◆		<p>Visualizing scenarios of use</p> <p>D</p>
	◆	◆			<p>Conceptual demonstrators showing conversion techniques</p> <p>S, D</p>
			◆		<p>Sketches to illustrate possible concepts</p> <p>D</p>
			◆		<p>Conceptual demonstrators representing small-scale 2D design mock-ups</p> <p>D</p>
			◆	◆	<p>"Productified" 3D demonstrators expressing luxurious and playful for a given product segment</p> <p>S, D</p>

(S=Scientists, D=Designers)

◆ ◆ ◆ the larger the diamond the more relevant to the STAM phase

Figure 4. Two of the concepts from the Bio-based Clothes Covers project, one immediately implementable (left) and one medium to long-term future concept realizable within 2-5 years (right) requires development of the bio-based materials proposed.

The project produced a number of concepts, one that was investigated for commercial production by the company. In addition to concepts that were immediately possible, a number of concepts that utilized materials under development were also suggested. These would be made from fully bio-based materials, but required a certain level of development in terms of large scale production to be available to the company. Figure 4 shows the immediately implementable concept and the material demonstrator for the fully bio-based material concept available in the medium to long-term future (2-5 years).

Conclusions

The TechMark Arena 2015 increased our knowledge about bio-based materials and how they are experienced. Eight students focused on this theme from different perspectives. We were able to benchmark new bio-based materials against materials being used in the marketplace for different applications. One material group was used to benchmark the opinions of the experts in a market segment against those of consumers not working in this area.

Material demonstrators are an important part of the process of exploring what new materials can do and how they can be designed into products. Abstract demonstrators were used as a means to assess the effect of different processing steps. It is important to align material tactile and visual properties with desired properties as early on as possible. We found the MoM method to be useful in guiding the development of material demonstrators. Conceptual demonstrators served to communicate material properties and ideas for potential use and inspired one invention disclosure that became a patent application. Productified demonstrators elicited positive comments about product design but can also be used to communicate limitations and improvement potential of both the material and its processing. Demonstrators showed the utility of establishing an iterative process from the start. They also allowed the student and supervisory teams to benefit from having something tangible at the center of their discussions

and discovery. The classification of the material demonstrators in different STAM phases allowed us to assess the roles of scientists and designers in bridging the research-to-market gap.

Initially, we considered TRLs to be rather straightforward, with research-oriented projects falling on the low end (TRL 2-3) and innovation-oriented projects falling on the high end (around TRL 7-8). From the projects exemplified here, the research-oriented Material Identity Crisis project produced some results that had a higher TRL: a patent application with materials tested in laboratory environment, TRL 4. This happened much faster than we would have anticipated. Furthermore, the innovation-oriented Bio-based Clothes Covers project produced some concepts having a lower TRL (future demonstrator using fully bio-based materials, TRL 5 due to development need). This established concrete market needs for material development, also sooner than we anticipated. We found that by concentrating on a common theme, bundling research-oriented and innovation-oriented projects created synergies that were unforeseen, including a vaguely defined pipeline for future development of bio-based materials. This implies that given the right framework, the research-to-market gap can be decreased as a result of faster testing in a lab environment coupled with identification of future market needs for specific materials. The benefits of bundling research-oriented and innovation-oriented projects will be further investigated in upcoming TechMark Arenas.

The teams were multidisciplinary on both sides with supervisors working in areas ranging from psychology and material development to industrial design and innovation. Students came from four different institutions at three universities. We believe it was this interaction on many fronts that led to the successful outcome of the TechMark Arena. New bio-based materials will be crucial in the bioeconomy. Understanding them and how material demonstrators can be used to show potential applications will make the research-to-market gap a little narrower. The development and demonstration of new bio-based material concepts and products was iterative and therefore the process benefits from the interaction of scientists and designers knowledgeable in different disciplines.

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The experience of an experience

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Abstract This paper examines a popular phenomenon that allows us to see ourselves from various perspectives, and allows us to perpetuate moments enabling us to relive experiences in a different state of mind or at a different time. To examine the phenomenon of experiencing an experience hermeneutic phenomenological research was employed. The empirical data gathered in relation to this research emphasizes the experience of own experience. On a daily basis we create and are exposed to, what I have termed, the secondary experience (Exp²), which occurs when we review a video and/or pictures we have taken.

I found there was a residual quality to Exp², which was malleable and unique to the individual. This element of malleability and the opportunity to design or redesign our memories is a marketable concept. The findings from the empirical data are comprised into a model, Path of Considerations (PoC), which is a tool to create a particular mindset, in the developer, to generate a new way of thinking. This model is dynamic by nature and although it is not completed in every branch, it is complete in relation to experiencing your own experience. A company can apply the PoC to gain insight into primary and secondary experiences.

Keywords Experiences, Memories, Storytelling

Introduction

In the row in front of you at the movie theater, a group of girls are cramming together to take a group Selfie. This reminds you that you want to post a picture of your outrageously large candy bag to Instagram. When you open the app the assortment of pictures of a fashion blogger's Instagram profile is open. A light flashes and you hear an "Ups!" whispered. The person next to you is taking a snap of his movie tickets.

A current phenomenon of our times is the fact that we are increasingly seeing ourselves from different perspectives often with the help of digital devices. It seems we seek the opportunities to further understand ourselves in order to gain a new level of understanding. This phenomenon is creating situations where we are experiencing our experiences differently and are giving experiences multiple layers of reflection. With the establishment of social media and the development of digital camera technology, it seems to be that the interest in how we perceive ourselves and how others perceived us has become more exercised and apparent.

Social media provides the platform for users to share who they are or what they aspire to be. Facebook launched a campaign the 4th of February 2016 in relation to their 12th anniversary, where they presented the user with a movie made up of pictures and quotes that have been posted on the user's Facebook wall through time (Bell, 2016). This is a creation of a secondary experience (Exp²) that was supposed to generate a nostalgic feeling in the viewer. However, if the material you share about your life on Facebook is limited the video of pictures will not have as powerful

an effect as intended. The other aspect of this commercial use of the Exp² is that if the algorithm which chooses the pictures, chooses the wrong pictures to present, such as pictures of ex-boyfriends, or people who have died, then the Exp² is a sad experience not something that will make the Facebook-user want to share the movie hashtagging it "Friendsday", which was Facebook's intention.

Even though the Exp² is something that we often experience and companies utilize, it has not been a phenomenon that has been researched further. This phenomenon is a large part of the everyday lives of younger generations, however the availability of cameras and the opportunity to preserve moments, also means that the older generations are becoming avid users of camera phones and thereby Exp². But, why do we want to take the pictures? What is the experience of looking at our pictures or others' pictures? The paper examines this phenomenon and seeks to establish a language in this area and to inspire further research. We seem to want to perpetuate experiences and with technology allowing us to do so with ease, we perpetuate as many moments as possible. This is a result of us not knowing which moments are valuable Exp². We remove our focus from the living of the experience to taking pictures of the experience, resulting in us not allowing ourselves to fully live the primary experience (Exp¹)...or we take too few pictures so we have limited material to generate a Exp². from later and we may with time forget what we actually experienced. This eagerness to perpetuate memories underlines the importance in understanding how the users use the products to satisfy this need as well as designing products that

not only cater to the Exp¹ but that also considers the user's experience during the Exp². The Exp² might in fact be the most important as it is the latest experience one can draw from.

What is the experience of an experience?

The experience of an experience (EoE) is the experience derived from another experience. It is when you relive or live an experience passively. The triggers for the EoE can be photographs, videos, concentrating on a sequence of memories, written work, diaries, products, concert T-shirts, drawings or a text message conversation. However, in this paper the EoE is mainly considered in relation to visual material, such as photographs and videos.

The secondary experience (Exp²) has so far been defined as the experience you have when looking at the visual material, the moment when an array of feelings and thoughts stream through your mind. The EoE is a general term for the whole situation and the Exp² is a term specific to that moment in the experience. Due to the breadth of the topic of interest this paper mainly focuses on the experience of own experience as the starting point to understanding the EoE, the hope is it will inspire others to explicitly explore other branches of the EoE and to build a language to facilitate communication and create a dialogue.

The term primary experience (Exp¹) is a term used in this paper to describe the original experience. The experience the person has had in person.

It must be noted, that the use of the word "secondary" to describe this passive experience, Exp², does not mean that the experiences are classified, thereby implying that these experiences are less than the primary experience. It is just to indicate that it builds on a previous experience.

The current understanding of experiences and secondary experiences

Through researching the experience of an experience (EoE), I came across a few researchers, whose work is relevant to exploring the EoE and presented an interesting aspect when considering this phenomenon. However, the topic of a secondary experience has had no found research devoted to it.

Kahneman (2011) does not define an experience, but rather focuses on the human dimension of experiences. He acknowledges that there are differences in cognitive processing during and after an experience. Kahneman (2011) describes this as the experiencing subject having two selves. The Experiencing Self, the self that is in the exact moment at the time of the experience. The second self, Kahneman (2011) described is the Remembering Self. This Self keeps score, makes choices, and builds the narrative of our lives. The Remembering Self is the more dominant of the two selves, meaning that the memories it keeps are the memories we base our decisions on and the memories it shapes are the memories we build our narratives on (Kahneman, 2011). Kahneman is not directly describing the EoE, but his description is relevant to consider in terms of understanding

memory building, narrative building and what thought processes are involved in the EoE.

Kahneman (2011) is not the only one addressing the notion of Self in relation to memory building and experiences. Damasio (2010) considers the experiencing body as the Self and the mind, with its cognitive functions. He terms this notion of Self, the Autobiographical Self, which has two states of processing, a conscious reflection and a non-conscious processing. Like Kahneman's two selves, the thought processing of the experience is the focal point in how experiences are remembered. *"As lived experiences are reconstructed and replayed, whether in conscious reflection or in non-conscious processing, their substance is reassessed and inevitably rearranged, modified minimally or very much in terms of their factual composition and emotional accompaniment."* (Damasio, 2010, pp. 149). Damasio's consideration of the Self mostly resembles Kahneman's Remembering Self.

In researching the theories related to EoE Kahneman's (2011) peak-end rule was discovered, which is relevant in regards to creating the right Exp². The peak-end rule implies that if something of significance happens at the end of the experience it can shift the impression of the entire experience for better or worse, despite the fact that it only accounts for a fraction of the entire experience (Kahneman, 2011). Thus, the Exp² can be a powerful tool for shaping our memories, manipulating our experiences or just making us aware of accidental manipulation.

The methodology of the research

The objective of the research for this paper is to gain a deeper understanding of the experience of experience (EoE) - a phenomenon that was uncovered while researching current applications and usages of drone technology in another research project. The study is therefore concentrated on why we desire looking at visual material of previous experiences. For example the way drones are being used for photography and extending the field of vision for humans. The EoE is not limited to visual material (videos, photos, social media) alone, even though it is not thoroughly researched the findings suggest that a secondary experience (Exp²) may also be triggered by other artifacts both tangible and intangible by nature (bicycles, relationships, architecture, clothes), as long as they spark an association with the user. As the focus of this research deals with a situation that is often taken for granted, the choice of methodology is important as it needs to question the common understanding surrounding why we want to take pictures and record videos. The methodology, in this study, also needs to acknowledge that there is no factual answer but rather a commonality and an essence to be found in an experience. In other words, the methodology needs to study the lived experience and all its dimensions.

In choosing a suitable method to further explore this phenomenon, a phenomenological hermeneutical method seemed appropriate as it tries to *"elucidate the essential meanings as it is lived experience"*

(Lindseth & Norberg, 2004, pp. 146). This phenomenon had not previously been researched and is not actively reflected upon in the public forum, it therefore requires a method of research that would allow for understanding the essential meaning of the phenomenon – a phenomenon that is so heavily present in our everyday lives - camera phones, Instagram, Snapchat, reality television, sports games on television etc.

Hermeneutic phenomenology is a methodology within, the philosophy of phenomenology (Coxon, 2014). Phenomenology, being a philosophy of Human Sciences, is the study of the lived experience, the nature, and meaning of the life-world humans experience (van Manen, 1997). In seeking to understand how the EoE affects humans, a methodology that supports the exploration of human experiences and allows for the complexity of humans to be accounted for must be employed. Phenomenology deviates from other science, because it is discovery oriented allowing the data to lead the way down unpredictable paths (Merleau-Ponty, 2012; van Manen, 1997). It is important that the methodology chosen supports explorative research as the focus of this study is previously unexplored. This requires the data to lead the way to discover something new. Van Manen (1997, pp.11) further underlines the appropriateness of phenomenology for this study by describing the distinction of phenomenology “...in that it does not aim to explicate meanings specific to particular cultures (ethnography), to certain social groups (sociology), to historical periods (history), to mental types (psychology) or to an individual’s personal life history (biology). Rather, phenomenology attempts to explicate the meanings as we lived them in our everyday existence, our lifeworld.” Phenomenology allows the researcher to gain insight into experiences, acknowledging that experiences are unique to the individual, while still identifying universally applicable essences of the experience (van Manen, 1997). Essences can also be described as the common traits of the experience (Lindseth & Norberg, 2004). The phenomenological approach puts an emphasis on the subjective meaning and usually reveals subjective levels of the experience, enabling the implicit to become explicit (van Manen, 1997). In the study of the EoE, the phenomenological philosophy is appropriate as it is assumed that the Exp² is an implicit subjective matter, which many people presumably do not actively reflect upon. One way to identify the essence of EoE is to use hermeneutic phenomenology. It allows for the interpretation and extraction of implicit meanings.

Hermeneutics is the interpretation and understanding of both linguistic and non-linguistic forms of expression (van Manen, 1997). Hermeneutically based research is considered interpretive research and must allow for the research to take unpredictable paths by allowing the findings to lead the way (Conroy, 2003). This enablement of the research allowing for the data to lead the way is in line with what is mention above, that in studying a previously uncharted area it is necessary to allow the data to speak.

In the realm of hermeneutics, there are several types

of hermeneutics. This theoretical framework builds on the Heideggian paradigm of interpreting and understanding phenomena with the help of the researchers ontological background.

Heidegger’s hermeneutic spiral of interpretation and understanding is a concept of the dynamic nature of our existence, it acknowledges that humans build their understanding and interpretation of a subject based on their ontological view, meaning their previous experiences throughout life (Conroy, 2003). When new information is gathered the interpretation and understanding of the subject will evolve (Conroy, 2003). The hermeneutic spiral was applied when trying to understand the participants and the experience. Each interview provided new information, and the ability to better understand the experience in the following interview. Each interview fed into the spiral of interpretation, enabling a better understanding of the EoE for the next interview.

One of the discussions about hermeneutics regards the bias a researcher may have when interpreting linguistic or non-linguistic expressions. Some philosophers suggest that the researchers’ ontological view is impossible to suppress and is needed to extract a deeper meaning from the material (Geanellos, 2000; van Manen, 1997). Together with Heidegger and Gadamer, Ricoeur also acknowledge that there is an ontological presence in all texts (Geanellos, 2000). Geanellos (2000) explains how Paul Ricoeur considered the interpretation to be the bridge between linguistic expression and lived experience. “This is especially so with research interviews where lived experience is expressed through language then transcribed into text and interpreted” (Geanellos, 2000, pp. 113). To avoid a biased interpretation, Paul Ricoeur’s method of objectification of transcribed interviews allows the researcher to move beyond the concept that there is only one correct understanding, and allows for several meanings to be identified in one linguistic expression, (Geanellos, 2000). Geanellos (2000, pp. 113) also terms this “textual plurality (that pre-understandings lead interpreters to interpret the same text faithfully yet differently), and multiplicity (that texts have many meanings) is acknowledged.” This issue is considered in the method, Seeing Tool (Coxon, 2008), used for interpretation of the transcribed interviews, by conducting several iterations of interpretation as well as broadening the researcher’s ontological view for a greater ability, to understand the context of meaning the interviewee is expressing himself in. This is elaborated on, below.

The design approach used in the study is Experience-based Design (XbD). XbD builds on hermeneutic phenomenology, which Van Manen (1997) describes as considering the whole aspect of being. To consider the human in their own world, Coxon (2014) lightly describes hermeneutic phenomenology as “It is both a philosophy (a way of thinking about how we live in the world) and a methodology (a way for us to begin to understand our experience of the world) It provides a sound framework for beginning to understand the nature of experience (ontologically) and how we might study it in some methodical way

(epistemologically)." The methods within XbD (SEEing Tool, embodiment) are derived with the above consideration of phenomenology and hermeneutic phenomenology in mind.

Methodology applied in practice

In understanding the EoE a literature study had been conducted identifying the segment of participants who were to be interviewed about their experience. Lindseth and Norberg (2004) Erwin (2012) and both emphasize the importance of gaining a shared understanding when understanding when communicating. In order to gain a common understanding and understanding the interviewees' frame of reference, the researcher employed embodiment. The researcher embodied several experiences to gain an insight into the subliminal sides of the experience in question.

The interviews were then conducted. Six participants were interviewed, each interview allowed for a deeper and overall understanding of the experience, to happen. As previously mentioned this study was a part of a larger research project in relation to approaching drone technology development from a Human-Centered perspective (Rasmussen, 2016). The participants chosen for interviews were in varying degrees familiar with recreational drones and had used them for recording adventure sports activities. The interviews discussed the experience and explicated the experience in accordance with Coxon's (2008) definition of experience, the Taxonomy of Experience. The interviews were conducted as explorative interviews, with naïve questioning the force the interviewee to explain as many elements as possible.

The interviews were then transcribed verbatim and processed through the SEEing Tool (Coxon, 2008), which is a method, through which several iterations of interpretation occur. The researcher assesses the several possible meanings of the text, groups them and then ends out in meaning structures or attributes of the experiences. These attributes were then assessed and patterns were identified organizing these attributes into a model, termed The Path of Consideration (PoC).

The benefit of using an explorative process is that it allows for the researcher to uncover unexpected information that can lead to new areas. By thoroughly understanding the phenomenon in question, which hermeneutic phenomenology allows, the developers will uncover deep insights of the customers motivations and product usage that could lead to great improvements of products or discovery of new business opportunities. In the study of the EoE, a model was developed, which enables designers and developers to map out an experience and in the process gain deep insights into the experience. The designers and developers will be approaching the development process with an open mind seeking opportunities that lie beyond the immediate user-product interaction, which could lead to profitable outcomes.

The research conducted in relation to this paper is preliminary. Therefore, the data currently gathered is concentrated around the Exp² gained from visual material acquired by cameras mounted on drones for the filming of adventure sporting activities. The data indicates that the phenomenon has multiple dimensions both in terms of different types of experiencing subjects and the types of artifacts that become triggers for a Exp². However, there are some issues to consider in regards to the research. These are, such issues as the findings being derived from a very specific segmented group of interviewees. The selected group of interviewees could raise concerns of the general application of the findings – can the PoC be used for gathering insights on the handle bar of a baby carriage? This question cannot be answered with certainty at this current stage. However, the findings suggest this might be possible if the PoC is modified a bit. The findings also suggest that these Exp² are different from Exp² initiated by visual material - the visual material confronts the you with reality in a deferent way. Nevertheless, there is some kind of passive experience in the form of associations happening beyond the immediate interaction with the product – this requires more research though.

Another issue is that the findings have not yet been tested, raising the issue that these findings may not be as universally applicable as expected. However, this project has been given a short time frame and few resources, which means that it is only top layer of the phenomenon that has been researched. This paper is therefore, merely suppose to encourage further research within the field and on phenomenon, and stimulate a more holistic view of the experience. This paper seeks to have developers and designers think of how the user interacts with a product beyond the immediate experience.

Four phases of the secondary experience

The empirical research's essential insights related to the impact of the experience of experience (EoE) were uncovered through an iterative data processing. These insights were found by analyzing the interpreted meanings derived from the empirical data. This was done to uncover deep layers of the experience, for much of the same reason Geanellos describes "*Methodologically, interpretation allows actualization of the meanings of a text...*" (Geanellos, 2000 pp.114). The meaning structures referenced in the methodology are actually the attributes, that have been further assessed and organized to provided the following findings.

Through the analysis there were different types of experiencing subjects identified and termed The Experiencer, the Viewer, and the Removed Experiencer (Table 1).

The analysis also provided an insight into there being different types of Exp² to be had depending on who is having the Exp². Each of these experiences has its own complex set of attributes. Therefore this paper is mainly focused on the Experience of Own Experience (Table 2).

Table 1. The types of experiencing subjects.

Type	Definition
The Experienter	A person who has lived the Exp1 himself/herself
The Viewer	A person watching the Exp2 who has not lived the Exp1 himself/herself
The Removed Experienter	A person who is experiencing the experience in real time but who is removed from the situation, such as Virtual Reality, First Person View drone operation (the video footage is streamed directly to a device) or live-streamed sports games.

Table 2. Types of secondary experiences.

Type	Definition
Experience of own experience	Experiencing something through video or photography that you have already experienced once before.
The Removed experience	Experiencing something you have been a part of yourself. This also includes experiencing Virtual Reality or other forms of being removed.

The main findings that the analysis uncovered were, that the EoE is a complex occurrence involving several intertwining phases. These phases defined as four phases of the EoE and were identified through the analysis, the *Primary Experience*, the *Evaluation*, the *Secondary Experience*, and the *Reflection*. Additional findings were gathered from the analysis and could be seen as attributes of a physical and meta-physical nature pertaining to the four phases of EoE. Table 3 provides a tabulated summary of the four phases and their related attributes.

The table presents attributes that were identified as being characteristic for the experience of own experience. These attributes were categorized in the phases that they had the most potent impact on.

The reason for the taking of pictures or video footage is to perpetuate something you felt in the moment that was worth perpetuating. However, what makes us look through those pictures again? An experience is not always interesting to relive, even though it allows you to understand the experience better. The determining factor of whether the experience is worth reliving is subjective. However, there are certain attributes of the Exp¹, that were identified as being reasons for the perpetuation of a Exp¹. Three types of purposes were identified for why someone might want to have a Exp². These purposes have been termed, Reflective, Reliving and Empathetic purpose. Table 4 explains the purposes in more detail.

The analysis has allowed of a deeper understanding of this phenomenon of taking pictures and recording video. However, these findings have an interrelated relationship that might not be apparent when just assessing the above information. In order to make these findings applicable the mapping tool, the Path of Consideration was engineered as a result.

The Path of Considerations

The key findings and the interrelationship of the insights of the analysis have been engineered into an actionable list of considerations, termed The Path of Considerations (PoC). If adopted by developers the PoC should enable them to gain greater insight into an

experience not only enabling them to design a product or an appropriate experience, but also allowing them to gain insight into what possible areas of innovation and development this phenomenon offers. An example of this could be the follow-me drones, that allows the Experienter to have an undisruptive experience. The secondary experience (Exp²) is the reason why you would continue to bring the drone with you time after time. Therefore, these companies need to consider what pitfalls there are in using the product and gain insights into the user's motivation for using a drone. Another example of the potential of PoC can be found in social media platforms. Gaining a greater insight into the users motivation for being active on these platforms can uncover insights that otherwise would have been overlooked opportunities. Other usages of the PoC can help uncover business opportunities in regards to the possible improvements to hardware or modifications of features based on the customer insights gathered from the PoC. An example of a different approach to the problem is by looking at the behavior that connects the Exp¹ with the Exp². There are communities of people using GoPro Cameras, who document much of their lives for the purpose of conveying an experience to another person or future self. But, in order to convey the essence of the experience there needs to be a certain level of skill to do so. Editing video footage was something that was mentioned during the interviews as being time consuming and therefore discouraging to do. This is an aspect for improvement. Can developers make editing software that gives you the ability to quickly edit your material, edit the audio, or automate you're picture taking, so your focus is devoted to the experience and not on perpetuating it. These suggested areas for improvement are not for the enthusiast but rather for the Experienter who wants to perpetuate the moment but not shift his focus to do so.

The PoC is supposed to help the developers to think beyond the initial experience and consider how to design for the related experiences that determine the survival and usage of the product. The PoC helps clarify the process and enables the designers and developers to gain a structured approach to understanding the phenomenon in question.

Table 3. The four phases of the experience of an experience.

Phase	Attributes
Primary Experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — The Exp¹ should be intense and engaging. — Unexpected happenings make the Exp¹ interesting to revisit emotionally. — Produce material, there must be someone taking pictures and capturing video. — Include unusual but appropriate camera angles, it tells the story of the exp. better. — Easily achievable angles, makes it so the experiencing subject can have the exp. — Undisrupted Exp¹, allows the experiencing subject to fully exp. the Exp¹ and not have to choose between the primary and secondary experience.
Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — The Exp¹ must have an element of significance, change, or unpredictability for you to desire a Exp². — Storytelling and shaping memories to color the story of your life. — Forgetting details and elements of the experience. — The time span between the Exp¹ and the Exp² has an influence on whether or not you want to relive an exp. or if you reflect upon behavior. — Editing video material and photographs enables and promotes self-awareness.
Secondary Experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Third person perspective generates an immediate reflective process. — Misperception of the experience and own self-image. — Reminded of physical and meta-physical elements of the experience. — Self-evaluation and self-judgment is heavily present in the Exp². — Exp² should include an element of novelty in some way otherwise we do not desire a Exp². — The material must communicate the experience or the desired message. — Exp² shape and solidify the memories we build and base the narrative of ourself on. — The Exp² must honor the Exp¹ or be better than the Exp¹ for the Exp¹ to be remembered positively. — When a Exp² is shared with others, we are sharing piece of our narrative.
Reflection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Exp² deepens your understanding of the Exp¹. — Memories shaped throughout the EoE, from the Exp¹ and Exp² melt together to shape one coherent memory. — A new perspective on things help shape a new and deeper understanding. — Exp² may provoke change or improvement of mannerism, performance etc. — We self-criticize before others can as a defense mechanism. — Memories become refreshed, strengthened or altered. — Easier for a viewer with previous experience with the Exp¹ to understand and fully appreciate the experience. — New details are discovered when having a Exp² with others.

Table 4. The Purpose for having a secondary experience.

The purpose	Definition
Reflective purpose	Have a desire to review the Exp ¹ from another perspective to gain more insight into the experience, this could be for the purpose of improving or bettering your abilities or mannerism or aesthetics.
Reliving purpose	Have a desire for reliving an element of change, unpredictability and/or something of significant value or meaning to you. To perpetuate an experience.
Empathetic purpose	Have a desire to understand an activity, a person, or even a place better by living someone else's Exp ²

The PoC only has a completed mapping of the Experience of Own Experience, but there is an opportunity for it to be expanded in relation to the other types of experiencing subjects, such as the Viewer and the Removed Experiencer. These expanded branches are drawn on the figure in order to clarify some of the findings from the analysis. The path presented is the Experience of Own Experience.

The first layer of considerations is to consider the types of experiencing subjects involved in the Exp² in question. The next layer is to understand what types of Exp² are relevant (Figure 1).

Then the developer assesses the purpose the Experiencer might be seeking(Figure 2). The analysis identified what appears to be a relation between time and what kind of purpose Experiencers have for having a Exp². If the Experiencer has a Exp² immediately after having a Exp¹ they will most likely reflect on their mannerisms, the activity, the

experience or their appearance, rather than seeking to relive the experience, which they clearly remember. However, if a longer amount of time, the duration of which has not been identified, has passed, the Experiencer will most likely be drawn into the experience again, reliving the excitement and energy. Therefore, when the element of time is added to the equation the purpose for the experience of a Exp², intended or not, may shift and take on a new meaning. As the point at which this shift occurs is individual to both the Experiencer and the experience, this gap cannot be quantified with a specific number of days, months or years.

The last layer of the PoC, is the layer in which the developers assess what the identified attributes of the Exp¹ and Exp² mean in this specific context and whether there are additional attributes to consider. Some of the most general attributes of the Exp¹ and Exp² are organized in a matrix, termed the Communication Matrix, see Table 5. This matrix

Figure 1. First and second layer of the Path Of Consideration.

Figure 2. The third layer of the Path of Consideration.

Figure 3. The fifth layer of the Path of Consideration the box of ideas for further development, opportunity areas for innovation etc.

illustrates how there are certain considerations to weigh if you intend to have a reflective purpose in the Exp². This matrix seeks to organize considerations that are relevant to consider in order for the communication of the experience to be optimal for a reflective or reliving purpose during the Exp². As mentioned above, the amount of time required before someone shifts from having a reflective purpose to a reliving purpose is individual to the person and the experience. This matrix can help lessen this variable by customizing the communication of the experience to a certain purpose or if the developers have identified that the Experiencers tend to have a reliving purpose the visual material can be guided towards that purpose.

The matrix provides some attributes related to each type of purpose grouped in relation to Exp¹ and Exp². When applying the matrix to a specific example the developer should not draw up a matrix but rather just list the relevant attributes and consider their meaning in relation to the context. This specific part of the Path of Consideration should generate some ideas that

would foster these attributes. These ideas are listed in the last box (Figure 3).

The PoC is not comprised of considerations that will secure a well-developed Exp² but rather it will provide a way to open up the understanding of the EoE. Developers may not agree with all the attributes, but they initiate a thought process about the Exp². With this model developers who adopt the PoC will, to a certain degree, be clearer about their targets for development and possibly uncover areas of opportunity that were not otherwise apparent because the path of the user experience was not considered. This PoC is not tested but provides a starting point for further work in this direction.

Conclusion

This paper comprises the results of a larger study that focuses on the very same topic (Rasmussen, 2016). The intention of the paper is to start a discussion about a phenomenon that is not currently discussed in relation to product development. The paper also seeks to start establishing a language that can facilitate this

Table 5. Communication Matrix, the fourth layer of the Path of Considerations.

	Reflective Purpose	Reliving Purpose
Primary experience	— Third person perspective	— Variation of camera angles
	— Provide an overview of the exp. with the use of camera angles.	— Produce and plan material for a Exp ²
	— Authentic behavior by uninterrupted experiences.	— Some staged situations are beneficial
	— The Experincer must be in the pictures and video material.	— Allow for false perception
Secondary Experience		— Element of impact (wow-factor)
		— Should be in the frame
		— Remember the setting of the exp. for later editing if needed
	— Misperception of self-image	— Video must communicate the exp.
	— Realizing new details	— Must remind the Experincer of the Exp ¹ (must transport us)
	— Provide something new (novelty)	

discussion and aid in communicating its findings. The phenomenon of experiencing previous experiences is something that happens many times a day, especially with the introduction of social media. We seem to want to perpetuate experiences, but because we don't know which are valuable secondary experiences (Exp²) we tend to either take too many pictures, so we do not allow ourselves to fully live the primary experience (Exp¹) or we take too few so we do not allow ourselves to have a Exp².

By employing phenomenological research, using interviews and hermeneutic analysis of the transcripts, a great amount of insight was gained. The scope of the EoE is very large so the main focus of this paper has been to understand the experience of own experience. The analysis provided a great amount of insight, into the fact that there are four phases of the experience of experience, The Primary Experience, The Evaluation, The Secondary Experience and The Reflection. Each phase has numerous meta-physical and physical attributes explaining certain elements of the part of experience pertaining to that phase. To make these attributes of the phases and additional attributes of the EoE applicable and structured, the Path of Consideration (PoC) was created to visualize the interrelation between the various attributes. The PoC is not a model that will provide developers with a perfectly engineered Exp² but will allow developers, and researchers to dive into a phenomenon gaining a better understanding of what experiences products give that involve a Exp².

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Do we really know which vehicle attributes are important for customers?

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Abstract The automotive industry is facing multiple challenges. Moving towards more environmentally friendly vehicles, new models of vehicle ownership, and associated changes in consumers' expectations and attitudes are amongst the most significant ones. Understanding how these trends are affecting customers' expectations is fundamental for attracting and retaining consumers. Although researchers have explored automotive purchase factors for many years, there appears to be little agreement regarding the relative importance of these factors, and often incomplete and contradicting findings are observed.

This paper reports preliminary findings from two studies designed to better understand vehicle attributes influencing customers' purchase decisions and satisfaction. The first study consisted of a review of sources to develop a comprehensive overview of relevant and clearly defined vehicle attributes describing the automotive product. The resulting list was applied in a second study to evaluate in an automotive context the idea that the importance of product attributes varies throughout the customer journey. Results indicated that the relative importance of vehicle attributes dramatically differed depending on the stage within the customer journey. The findings are discussed in the context of managing the product evaluation and development process.

Keywords *Customer satisfaction, Product attribute, Customer journey, Purchase factors, Automotive*

Introduction

Technology has changed every aspect of our lives, including the way we purchase products. Online comparison tools provide a quick and easy way to compare and evaluate complex products, such as vehicles. Customers seeking to purchase a new vehicle no longer rely on information provided solely by a dealer. They conduct their own research and try to predict how the actual product would perform and thus, reduce the risk from their decision (Cui, Lui, & Guo, 2012).

The way customers purchase vehicles has also changed. Personal lease plans are the preferred mechanisms for the majority of new car buyers: (Whichcoul, 2016). However, these customers rarely turn into owners. In a similar way, people living in urban areas where traffic, demand for parking spaces and cost of ownership are high, purchasing a vehicle may not be attractive. Companies like Zipcar, Car2Go, City Car Club and Uber provide a variety of options to use a "pay-as-you-go" car (e.g. Rogowsky, 2016). Together, these trends indicate a shift from purchasing a mobility product towards purchasing Mobility As A Service (MAAS) (Godlevskaja et al. 2011, Eurotransport 2014). Nevertheless, however, customers still need to make a decision what vehicle to choose although the

relative importance of vehicle attributes may be changing as a consequence of these developments.

Given the changes currently disrupting the automotive industry, it becomes increasingly necessary to capture and understand customer concerns, such as needs, motives, and values (Desmet, 2003) in order for automotive products to stay relevant. Understanding customers, however, is challenging as their judgements are based on subjective reasoning (Reid, Frischknecht, & Papalambros, 2012). Previous studies have proposed frameworks for designers to target specific aspects of product design that consumers perceive in products (Noble & Kumar, 2010) and translate consumer responses towards specific vehicle attribute into actionable engineering aspects (Yadav and Goel 2008). The "House of Quality" is an example of this approach, though which consumers' subjective responses are targeted by measurable engineering characteristics, likely to influence those responses (Hauser and Clausing 1988). This method classifies consumers' responses, or attributes, depending the level of detail – primary (e.g. Good appearance), secondary (e.g. Interior Trim), tertiary (e.g. attractive non plastic look), etc. (Hauser and Clausing 1988). However, for this approach to be successful it is imperative to understand which attributes are important for which

customers and when.

For years, companies such as Cap Gemini, JD Power, Trend Tracker, KPMG, Harris Interactive, have conducted large-scale consumer surveys with the aim of capturing relative importance of various vehicle attributes over consumers’ purchase decision. However, the relative importance of vehicle attributes is still far from clear. Contradictions and issues were observed with regard to the vehicle attributes used in these studies examples of which are illustrated in Table 1. To ease comparison, only two sources for each year were selected, with their top three important attributes. The sources were compared considering the following aspects: 1) year of data collection, 2) method used and location, and 3) important vehicle attributes.

As can be seen in Table 1, for 2011, Cap Gemini (2011) reported that reliability of a brand was the most important attribute followed by safety and vehicle price. KPMG (2011), on the other hand, reported fuel efficiency, safety innovation and vehicle styling as the top three important factors. Similar contradictions can be observed for 2015. Auto Trader (2015) ranked colour, size, and brand as most important while Harris-Interactive (2015) ranked cost of purchase, fuel efficiency, and overall quality as the most important purchase factors.

Adoption of different attribute terms such as “safety” (Cap Gemini 2011) and “safety innovation” (KMPG 2011) creates uncertainty as to whether these terms refer to the same attribute. Typically, no descriptions

Table 1. Contradictions in relative importance of attributes across consumer studies.

	Method	Rank	Important purchase factors (attributes)
Cap Gemini 2011			
Data collected 2011	Survey	1	Reliability of brand
	Global	2	Safety
		3	Price of vehicle
KPMG 2011			
Data collected 2011	Survey	1	Fuel efficiency
	Global	2	Safety innovation
		3	Vehicle styling
Auto Trader 2015			
Data collected 2015	Survey	1	Colour
	UK	2	Size
		3	Brand
Harris-Interactive 2015			
Data collected 2015	Survey	1	Cost of purchase
	UK	2	Fuel efficiency
		3	Overall quality

Source: Cap Gemini website, (Cap Gemini, 2011), KPMG website (KPMG, 2011), Auto Trader (Auto Trader 2015), Harris Interactive website (Harris Interactive 2015)

or definitions of these attributes are provided, which renders their meaning ambiguous. Evaluation of attributes in different level of detail, also creates obstacles in comparison. An attribute as vehicle styling (KPMG 2011) target primary attribute category (Hauser and Clausing 1988). The colour attribute (Auto Trader 2015), however, is a tertiary attribute, as it could be positioned, within the vehicle styling (primary attribute), exterior (secondary), colour (tertiary). Evaluation of vehicle attributes with different level of detail may leave gaps to how important were other aspects of vehicle styling to consumers, beside colour.

Comprehensive review of the vehicle attributes reported from Cap Gemini (2011) and KPMG (2011), presented in Table 2, create an impression that not all vehicle attributes were evaluated. Cap Gemini considered the price of the vehicle, emissions and brand name, while KPMG did not report the importance of these attributes. Similarly, KPMG reported the importance of ergonomics and comfort and telematics attributes, which were not presented in Cap Gemini’s report.

The difference in importance of attributes presented in these studies may be a result of different sample sizes and sample characteristics such as type of consumer groups. It could also be a result from incomplete attribute evaluation, as observed in Cap Gemini and KPMG reports or be related to selective reporting of attributes (e.g. top 9 most important attributes (KPMG 2011)). The difficulty in comparing studies is further amplified by the different terminology used to refer to supposedly the same attribute (e.g. “safety” and “safety innovation”), which may or may not differ. Comparisons, in such cases, may not be valid. Collectively, all of the discussed issues make comparisons between studies problematic.

Table 2. Full list of important vehicle attributes reported by Cap Gemini (2011) and KPMG (2011).

Rank	Important purchase factors	
	Cap Gemini 2011	KPMG 2011
1	Reliability of brand	Fuel efficiency
2	Safety	Safety innovation
3	Price of vehicle	Vehicle styling
4	Fuel Economy	Environmental friendliness
5	Quality of exterior styling	Ergonomics and comfort
6	Quality of interior styling	Build-in navigation, technologies, etc.
7	Extra options at no cost	Telematics/ personal assistance services
8	Product features/options to fit your needs	Use of alternative fuel technologies
9	Low emissions	Enhanced vehicle lifespan
10	Brand name	

Source: Cap Gemini website, (Cap Gemini, 2011), KPMG website (KPMG, 2011)

The available academic literature does not clarify which attributes are important for automotive customers either. Actually, comparisons between academic studies and industry reports were found to be even more difficult to make. This is partly due to the fact that academic studies focus on specific subjects such as the evaluation of attributes for a specific brand (e.g. Stylidis, Hoffenson, Wickman, & Söderman, 2014; Waligóra & Waligóra, 2007), one specific attribute evaluated in depth – e.g. product aesthetics (Yadav, Jain, Shukla, Avikal, & Mishra, 2013), sound quality (e.g. Cerrato, 2009) or target specific part of the automotive product as interior dashboard (Ahmed & Yannou, 2013; Huertas-Leyva, 2011), or vehicle seats (Erol, Diels, Shippen, Richards, & Johnson, 2014). An additional complication is the effect of time. In academia, often the year of publication is not the same as the year responses were collected due to the long period of time required for publishing or because researchers analysed previously collected responses (e.g. Baltas and Siridfakis 2013, Choo and Mokhtarian 2004). As the importance of vehicle attributes also reflect trends, economic status, political issues, and technological developments by the time findings reach publicity, they are already dated. Furthermore, vehicle attributes used in academic studies suffered from the same issues found in industry reports. Although references from these studies clearly stated the sources from which these attributes were derived, these attributes were also dated.

Relevant and comprehensive attributes describing modern vehicles were not found in either academic literature or recent industry reports. Therefore, the development of a comprehensive and well-defined list of vehicle attributes is necessary to fully capture what is actually important to customers.

Attribute importance over time

Attribute importance is measured with aim to identify which vehicle attributes are important to customers and influence their purchase decision (pre-purchase attribute importance) (e.g. Harris Interactive 2015), or evaluate the satisfaction of the vehicle during ownership (post-purchase attribute importance) (e.g. JD Power customer satisfaction studies). The common model of pre and post purchase stage of the customer journey, used to explore how attribute importance vary over time (e.g. Mittal, Katrichis, & Kumar, 2001), may no longer be sufficient. Whereas in the past, the pre-purchase stage was largely related to a dealer visit, today it is preceded by individual research, largely spent online (Syncapse, 2013). As a consequence, the customer journey could be separated into 3 phases – research, dealer visit and ownership.

Research (indirect product evaluation)

The evaluation of the product at this stage is based on information presented in a numerical format as vehicle dimensions, internal space, and fuel consumption figures. High-quality images and virtual 3D models assist in gaining insight how the product would look like in reality (e.g. Nissancouk, 2016; Fordcouk, 2016). The access to owner's reviews assists customers to predict what ownership would be like

and decrease the risk in their decision (Cui et al., 2012).

During the research stage, although limited from sensory experience, customers use visual cues as much as possible to try and predict certain product qualities (Creusen and Schoormans, 2005). Although virtual and interactive environment could compensate in a way for the absence of information from other senses, rich emotional experiences are difficult to achieve compared to direct, in-person product evaluation is able to do (Schifferstein and Spence n.d.).

Dealer visit (direct product evaluation)

During a dealer visit, consumers have the chance to experience a chosen product in person. Such evaluation consists of simultaneous sensory experience, which can create powerful impact over the customer (ref). This experience can be relatively short in time, however, during which the customer has to predict whether the product will satisfy the various needs. Taking into consideration the complexity of modern vehicles, certain aspects of the car might be difficult to be predict in the longer term (e.g. intuitiveness of the infotainment system). Furthermore, a vehicle can be experienced in a static mode (in the showroom), and in dynamic mode (a test drive)(Abbott, 2009) . At a dealer, where customers perceive a lot of information, from all their senses, across different aspects of the vehicle, may create the perception of so much information in relatively short time overwhelming result in remembering little details, or key attributes (Schifferstein and Spence n.d.).

Post purchase (routine product interaction)

With a purchase, customers enter a long term relationship with their chosen product, the product manufacturer, and the dealer providing the after purchase customer service. During this stage, customers interact with the product more frequently, executing routing operations, discovering more details about the purchased vehicle, creating memories. With time, the owner may develop affection and even feel attached to the car (Dant, 2004; Sheller, 2004). Main contributors to attachment were found to be related to exceptional functionality of a product or memories built through product's lifecycle (Mugge, Schifferstein, & Schoormans, 2010). Product attachment and affection can be powerful tools used in favour in strengthening the customer-brand relationship (Kumar, Townsend and Vhrhies, 2014; Mugge, Schifferstein, & Schoormans, 2010), and influence re-purchase (Baltas and Saridakis, 2013).

Thus, the way consumers search for their new vehicle today, as supported by both academic and industry research studies, create indirect and direct product evaluations occurring during online research and dealer visit respectively. Following on from this, the customer journey can be separated into 3 stages – research, dealer visit, and ownership. To date, the reviewed academic literature and industry research studies, have failed to recognise this division of the customer journey into the proposed 3 staged customer journey. It therefore has also failed to explore how

attribute importance may change during the different stages of the customer journey.

To test whether such differentiation of the customer journey is valid, relevant up to date vehicle attributes are needed. Therefore, Study 1 was designed to develop comprehensive and well-defined list of vehicle attributes. The list was then applied in a second study to explore how these attributes change over the hypothesised stages of product experience in the customer journey.

Study 1: Development of a vehicle attributes list

Aim and methodology

The aim of this study was to develop a comprehensive list of vehicle attributes which could be applied for the evaluation of modern vehicles. Due to the existing gap between perception of attributes from consumers and industry professionals, the list of vehicle attributes was aimed to achieve an acceptable level of understanding from both consumers and industry professionals.

A deductive approach was adopted with the aim to identify all relevant vehicle attributes from all levels of detail and the variety of terms used to refer to them. The selection of these attributes was irrespective of the aims or purpose of the reviewed studies. This allowed identification attributes with different level of detail. Five main information sources were used: academic literature, industry reports, automotive magazines, automotive websites and manufacturer's brochures. The reviewed academic literature covered a variety of research fields such as marketing, ergonomics, product development psychology (e.g. Wiseman, 1971; Choo and Mokhtarian, 2004; Yadav and Goel, 2008; van Rijnsoever, Farla and Dijst 2009; Baltas and Saridakis 2013, Wu, Liao and Chatwuthikrai, 2014). Industry reports included freely accessible reports published by Auto trader, Cap Gemini, JD Power, KPMG, Harris Interactive and Trend Tracker. The selection of automotive magazines and websites, was based on the most purchased magazines for 2014 in the UK - Top Gear, What Car?, Auto Express and Autocar (Mediaweekcouk, 2014) and most visited websites for 2015 in the UK - AutoTrader.co.uk, Motors.co.uk, Parkers.co.uk, Car Buyer.co.uk (Alexacom, 2015). The two best-selling manufactures for 2015 – Ford and Vauxhall were selected to explore attributes used in their brochures and websites. The developed draft attribute list was verified through consumer and expert interviews conducted in 2015, in the UK.

Procedure

Temporary categories were created to group synonyms referring to the same attribute (e.g. Appearance, Styling, Design, Aesthetics). The most appropriate and accurate attribute term in the automotive context was used to define the primary attribute category. Once the primary category was defined, the same approach was used to define relevant secondary attributes. This procedure was repeated for all temporary categories.

To verify the developed list of vehicle attributes, create relevant attribute definitions with acceptable level of understanding from both consumers and industry professionals, 13 consumers and 3 expert were interviewed. To avoid single word responses from participants and receive a comprehensive explanation about the various attributes, adaptation of the laddering technique was used. This technique has been used to explore how consumers' interpret product attributes into personal values and associations (Reynolds & Gutman, 1988). In the context of this study, this technique was used to capture core aspects of primary attributes and to explore their respective secondary attributes. To ease analysis, each interview was recorded and later transcribed.

Participants

Thirteen volunteers participated for this study, from which 10 were male. Participants owned/leased vehicles of different sizes (vehicle segment) and ranged from affordable mainstream brands to luxury premium brand vehicles, purchased brand new or second hand, under private or in a company scheme. None of the participants who volunteered for this study received monetary rewards but they were offered snacks and drinks to minimise the formality of the interview, and increase their willingness to share more details. The experts from different expertise in the automotive industry – vehicle dynamics, ergonomics and human factors.

Analysis

Nvivo, a software for qualitative data analysis, was used to import transcribed recordings and group responses for each attribute. The analysis consisted in comparison of primary and secondary attribute categories formed as result of literature with consumers' and experts understanding of these attributes. The definitions for each attribute were a combination of consumers' own definitions, dictionary definitions in automotive context, experts' definitions and the interviewer's own knowledge.

Results

The various sources used to identify relevant vehicle attributes, revealed that an attribute strongly related to technological development, has not yet been considered among vehicle attributes. Security, or more specifically cyber security, although receiving significant attention in all industries, including the automotive one, was still portrayed by manufacturers as locking mechanisms, alarms and immobilisers (e.g. Fordcouk, 2016, Mercedes-benzcouk, 2016, Peugeotcouk, 2016). Cap Gemini (2014) reported that although consumers are willing to share private data, they also express concern about who has access to it. This attribute has not yet been reported as important for customers purchasing new vehicles and perhaps not considered for evaluation so far. The increased software development in vehicles and connectivity features creates vulnerabilities similar to those that mobile devices and laptops have been experiencing for years – viruses, hacking, data gathering, and monitoring. With the recent evidence of software hacking on a Nissan Leaf (BBCcouk, 2016) and Tesla's malfunction on the self-driving feature (Ghoshal,

2016), security and data protection and associated attributes are likely to become increasingly important in the near future.

Once all primary attributes were identified, the outcomes of the interviews, assisted in aligning the secondary attribute categories into the respective primary attributes and defining each primary attribute category. The most difficult attributes to classify were safety, human-machine interface and vehicle dynamics. The challenges derived from the secondary attributes, as some of them could be classified under different primary attribute category. For example, the advanced driving assistance systems (ADAS), could be classified in both safety and in car technology. Because ADAS has been designed to prevent accidents, the most appropriate classification for ADAS, supported from experts, was in the safety category (Table 3). In-car technology, infotainment systems and human-machine interface were terms often used to refer to the user-interface through which consumers could manipulate various vehicle systems. However, in-car technology and infotainment were found to be inappropriate descriptors for this category. Consumers understanding of the term in-car technology was inconsistent, as participants referred to various aspects of the vehicle as ABS safety feature, journey guidance (Sat Nav) and ADAS functions. Infotainment on the other hand, was not an appropriate term, as it represents commodity rather than an attribute (e.g. vehicle's brakes are commodity, braking is an attribute). Human-Machine interface (HMI), was the most appropriate term to describe the software aspects of the vehicles which provide user access to various vehicle functions. Vehicle dynamics, was an attribute category, which covered the in-motion aspects of the vehicle. The automotive experts had strong view on how this category should be structured, however, consumers participating in the study, did not perceive this attribute the same way and in such detail. For this reason, the secondary attributes, defined under vehicle dynamic, were based on the considerations from all reviewed sources used in this study and researcher's own judgement, to create acceptable level of understanding of these attributes from both consumers and industry experts. All primary attribute categories, their respective secondary attributes and developed descriptions are presented in Table 3.

Study 2. Attribute importance throughout the customer journey

Aim and methodology

The purpose of the second study was to test whether division of the customer journey to 3 stages would be valid and explore how the importance of vehicle attributes varies across the 3 stages. The same participants from Study 1 took part in this study.

Procedure and analysis

Prior to the interviews, participants were informed that the interview would discuss their past purchase experiences. This allowed participants to remember these particular events, ahead of the interview. During the interview were participant asked to freely describe

their purchase experience and satisfaction from their current vehicle. To ensure, step by step approach, the interviews were semi-structured, and the questions were used to guide participants to a specific stage in their customer journey and explore it in detail. The analysis reflected the importance of primary attributes, analysed through Friedman's two-way analysis of variance in Spss.

Results

The outcomes of this study support the ideas that there is a difference between the two pre purchase stages (research and dealer visit), and that the split of the customer journey to 3 stages – research, dealer visit and ownership is valid. This was confirmed by the types of attributes evaluated specifically between the research and dealer visit stage. Attributes requiring direct product evaluation, such as comfort, were not considered by participants during the research stage, but were highly important at the dealer stage (see Table 4). Practicality was an attribute, which was important for participants in both the research and the dealer visit stage. However, during their research stage participants built only expectations for practicality of the vehicle, but could only evaluate the actual practicality at the dealer. Depending how closely their expectations were met from the actual product, would guide consumers' responses (Participant A).

"...we selected the cars we liked but when we went to the dealer, we discarded the other two as they were too cramped at the back"

Participant A

As opposed to expectations prior to Study 2, the importance of Vehicle Dynamics scored low in importance at the dealer, where participants were able to explore the various aspects of this attribute in-person. During ownership, however, this attribute became important (see Table 4).

Other aspects of the vehicle, which were not evaluated prior to purchase, become evident during the ownership stage and routine interaction.

"...the given figures stated that the fuel consumption was good...but in reality it was not good at all..."

Participant D

"...now you realise that on the weekends it will be more expensive....and...it is a challenge to drive it on electric engine (Hybrid Vehicle)"

Participant E

"...the back seats are quite spacious. I only discovered that, when my family visited last year"

Participant G

Security was an attribute were not mentioned or considered by any of the participants. Perhaps it is something that people take for granted or maybe it is

Table 3. List of vehicle attributes covering primary attribute categories, their respective secondary attributes and definitions.

Attribute and sub-attributes	Attribute Definition
Reliability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Frequency of breakdown — Durability (e.g. Battery life) — Robustness 	The ability of a vehicle, which is regularly maintained, to perform to required standards over a set period of time. Strongly depended on its components and systems, within a vehicle which have to withstand repeat usage (Durability) or irregular extreme events (Robustness). Perception of reliability also derives from severity of breakdowns, Brand Image and owners' reviews.
Safety <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Active Safety (or ADAS), (e.g. blind spot detection, lane keeping) — Passive Safety (e.g. Airbags, seat belts, etc.) 	Vehicle's capabilities to prevent (active safety) an accident or protect its occupants from injury (passive safety), should an accident occur.
Security <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Physical Security (e.g. immobiliser, locks) — Cyber Security (e.g. Firewall) 	Resistance of the vehicle to physical criminal activities (as vehicle theft) or illegal penetration of vehicle's systems with the aim obtaining personal user data from the vehicle (cyber security).
Cost of ownership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Price (Monthly payments) — Running Costs (e.g. fuel consumption, tax) — Resale value (Depreciation) 	Costs associated with obtaining the vehicle, operating it during its lifecycle (running costs), and disposing of it (resale value).
Vehicle Dynamics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Ease of driving — Road Handling — Ride Quality — Performance 	Vehicle's behaviour while in motion, its responsiveness to input and feedback received during ride/drive.
Practicality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Boot (e.g. capacity, floor adjustability, size of boot door and boot opening) — Interior storage (e.g. glove box) — 3+ doors — 4+ seats — (flat) Foldable seats 	Vehicle's capacity and flexibility of components to allow fulfilment of various situations for which the vehicle may be used.
Comfort <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Driving Position — Seat Comfort — Interior quietness — Roominess (leg, head room front and rear) — Convenience (e.g. electric operation – mirrors; Driving Range, Recharging time EV) — Overall interior feel 	<p>The ability to have pleasant, pain free, driving/ riding position, allowing adequate reach and effortless operation of key controls for driver and all passengers.*</p> <p><i>* Some aspects of comfort depend on length of journey – e.g. long term comfort</i></p>
HMI (Human-machine interface) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Quality of infotainment system (e.g. screen resolution, responsiveness, intuitiveness) — Media (e.g. DVD, CD, DAB, SD, Sat Nav) — Connectivity (USB, Bluetooth, Wi-Fi) 	Integrated operating system, providing build-in journey assistance (navigation), media (e.g. radio) and connectivity options.
Build Quality* <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Craftsmanship <p><i>* Definition adapted from (Stylidis & Wickman, 2015)</i></p>	Build Quality (or Technical perceived quality) is a complex attribute, which consumers build toward vehicles, based on visual cues, interaction, tactile/auditory feedback and interior smell, developing impression toward the overall quality of the product.
Interior/ Exterior Styling <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Product Personality (Product Image) — Novelty — Design metaphors — Product forms (e.g. design principles – harmony, golden ratio, unity, symmetry) — Other – colours, colour combinations, textures, materials/ material combination, contrast 	Styling relates to vehicles' visual design (interior and exterior), through aesthetic principles (as symmetry, unity), that impact consumers' judgements regarding different product aspects as novelty and product personality, creating differentiation, appeal or desire.
Brand Image <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Country of origin — Brand equity* (e.g. Brand associations, personality) <p><i>* (Aaker, 1995)</i></p>	Brand image is the current perception consumers have toward specific brand, build through advertising, market positioning, personal experience, and brand equity aspects as personality, associations, etc.

difficult to evaluate.

Each attribute importance, and relevance for each stage of the customer journey is visualised in Table 4.

Discussion and implications

The implications of these studies could be used in various fields of research. The attribute list developed could be used by other researchers to ensure a complete and consistent evaluation of vehicle attributes. As technology develops constantly, this list should be updated as appropriate. To ensure consistent understanding of the evaluated attributes, clear descriptions containing the appropriate level of detail should be provided with the evaluation of various vehicle attributes.

The division of the customer journey into 3 stages enables us to understand how the importance of various attributes changes over time and with experience of using the vehicle. This might have implications, for example, for which attributes should be highlighted in marketing material and interactions at the dealership. It also gives an understanding of which attributes are most likely to drive brand loyalty in the longer term. The importance of these attributes may also differ between different groups of consumers (e.g. based on demographics or attitudes to cars and driving) and across different sectors of the car market (e.g. luxury, sports, family, budget). Moving forward, these are issues that we plan to evaluate in more depth.

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Table 4. Attribute importance across the 3 customer journey stages.

Vehicle Attributes	Pre-Purchase		Post-Purchase
	Research	Dealer visit	Ownership
Interior /Exterior Styling	*****	*****	*****
Cost of ownership	*****	*****	*****
Practicality	*****	*****	*****
Comfort	*****	*****	*****
Vehicle Dynamics	*****	*****	*****
Reliability	*****	*****	*****
Build Quality	*****	*****	*****
Safety	*****	*****	*****
HMI	*****	*****	*****
Brand Image	*****	*****	*****
Security	*****	*****	*****

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Lempi: “do you remember that moment there?” Nonverbal stories of memorable locations in long-distance relationships

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Abstract Nonverbal communication (NVC) is the richest way for people to emotionally express themselves. However, in computer-mediated communication (CMC) NVC is underused. People in long-distance relationships (LDRs) already know how to adapt to CMC. While CMC is considered to be less ideal, LDRs still have a tendency to disclose more intimacy, closeness and relatedness to each other than non-LDRs. As CMC has been mainly designed for business purposes, there is an opportunity to target relatedness experiences and a challenge to find inter-relatedness of the daily activities of LDRs. The key question is: Which attributes do NVC-products need to have to evoke an enriched experience of relatedness for LDRs?

This phenomenological research exposes meaningful experiences and stories that can be expressed via adaptation to NVC. Prototypes were built via iterations around NVC-product attributes to trigger intended relatedness experiences. The diary study and in-depth interviews disclosed a broad range of valuable stories about feeling related at a distance. Suggestions are made on how to apply these attributes and stories when designing for both richer verbal and nonverbal communication experiences. The attributes and stories of Lempi are also useful for further research to deeper understand how people can communicate in more meaningful ways.

Keywords *Nonverbal communication, Long-distance relationships, Relatedness, Meaningful locations, Experience design*

Introduction

Communication is necessary to be maintained within any relationship (Aylor, 2003). One experiences closeness and intimacy by disclosing feelings and emotions to each other. People want to connect regularly with others who care about them to feel intimate and fulfill the need of relatedness (Sheldon et al., 2001, p. 339, cited in Hassenzahl, Heidecker, Eckoldt, Diefenbach, & Hillmann, 2012).

Intimacy requires two components: the sharing of emotions and inter-relatedness of daily activities (Guldner, n.d.). Nonverbal communication (NVC) is the easiest way to express emotional and relational information that is not present in spoken and written language (Trenholm, 1999). “Our nonverbal behavior towards someone is heavily influenced by the bond we feel with the other person” (Janssen, IJsselsteijn, & Westerink, 2010 p. 3). This is also described in the equilibrium theory by Argyle (1965): “The closer people are related to each other, the more nonverbal behavior is possible to be exchanged. When a stranger intrudes you personal space nonverbal behavior will change to keep the balance in the intimacy equilibrium.”

Technology focuses on the transmission of explicit information while subtle and emotional cues, typical for close relationships, are neglected (Hassenzahl et al., 2012). Couples in long-distance relationships

(LDRs) engage in more adaptive self-disclosure and form more idealized relationship perceptions than non-LDR couples do in the pursuit of intimacy across various computer-mediated communication (CMC) (Jiang and Hancock, 2013). Nevertheless, “inter-relatedness” remains a challenge (Guldner, n.d.).

People can connect differently through NVC (Triverio, 2011). NVC helps when partners do not have any stories to tell but they just want to feel close to each other when physically separated (Hassenzahl, 2011) and it can increase relatedness experience (Janssen, Bailenson, IJsselsteijn, & Westerink, 2010).

Implementing NVC provides a new medium with possibilities for new adaptations and future usage. This can radically improve the comfort and quality of the communication experience (Janssen, IJsselsteijn, & Westerink, 2010). Solutions should be “communication experiences” orientated rather than “mobile devices” (Hassenzahl, 2011). Hassenzahl (2010, p.8) defines an experience as: “an episode, a chunk of time, that one went through, sights and sounds, feelings and thoughts, motives and actions closely knitted together, stored in memory, labeled, relived and communicated to others. Experience is a story, emerging from dialogue of a person with her or his world through action”

Figure 1. Theoretical framework with attributes listed.

Research objective

This research aims to guide design for nonverbal relatedness experiences, the affective episodes or stories in which *LDR* partners feel close, related and intimate without using words. It is important to facilitate these experiences over a distance. The objective is to find out which attributes are necessary to evoke NVC experiences that make people feel related at a distance. The research studies the ways of getting the daily mundane untold stories told in a nonverbal way. This has been challenging within *CMC*, where functionality is mostly prioritized (Hassenzahl et al., 2012).

Attributes

For this study, more than 150 different physical and digital artifacts were evaluated, majority gathered by Hassenzahl et al. (2012). The different strategies for relatedness experiences cover awareness, expressivity, physicalness, gift giving, joint action and memories (Hassenzahl et al., 2012). The strategies help to see where there is a need for further research and development. This study takes into account also social psychology theories, such as uncertainty reduction theory, which focuses on “verbal and nonverbal communication between recipients and providers that reduces uncertainty about the situation, the self, the other, or the relationship” as noted by Albrecht and Adelman (1987, p. 19). Without managing relational uncertainty an interpersonal relationship cannot be sustained (Dainton & Aylor, 2001; Knobloch & Solomon, 1999). Uncertainty reduction ensures that partners commit and plan for a mutual future.

The artifact analysis resulted in product attributes that give guidance on how to design for a NVC experience. Attributes are tools for developing novel and improved concepts. They were listed within their

related field of study in a theoretical framework (Figure 1).

Artifact analysis highlighted the feasibility of the following attributes in particular. *Rich interaction* claims that physical interaction can be designed in such a way it is perceived intuitively, by unifying form, shape and interaction (Frens, 2006). This makes interaction meaningful with a possible extension to the message.

To make people change their behavior products need to stage an experience and be transformational (Halfon, 2007). Experiences can make people communicate in a different way. The *aesthetic of friction* (Hassenzahl, 2011) points out that experiences are transformational in themselves. These pleasurable troublemakers mock the multi-capable user by establishing a friction between your current and desired behavior (Hassenzahl & Laschke, 2015). Products with *hedonic quality* facilitate achievement of fundamental human needs, those beyond instrumental and action needs, such as being a caring partner and a part of each other’s life.

A *personal device* connects two partners together, like a ring. No one else has a similar device; it is unique and symbolizes the bond between the two. Yet, it is not an alarm going off and it always known who is sending the message. Being notified is not overwhelming. Such *unobtrusive* notification does not interrupt *Tangible* memories (Hassenzahl et al., 2012) are of great importance as by touching the object one can re-experience a mutual moment. Thus, one can get closer to the partner in a relative way through touching the product

Figure 2. Xsound Surprise effect, Secret language.

Figure 3. Xstress Support / Care, Simultaneously, Communal relationship.

Figure 4. Xplore Old reference, Daily routines.

Figure 5. Xview Old reference, Rich interaction.

Figure 6. XDancer Equity theory, Reciprocity.

Figure 7. Xtrude Related representation and participation, Simultaneously.

See them in action: <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLB0t8O0gQfOo8vfa9Asi3zyck3havD9-L>

Figure 8. A set of Lempi devices.

A NVC device is preferably wearable or hand-held instead of a stationary object or immense installation. The contact with the product resembles the contact one wants to have with the partner, near and carried along. With an *intimate mobile* device, one is not restricted to a certain location and the device can document the fresh experience.

Addressing a *different sense*, from vision, enables capturing experiences in novel ways, achieving a broad contact through other channels of NVC.

Instead of passive monitoring or demanding scheduling events, the product helps to register and *log* events during the day. Afterwards the user can select the most representative events.

In the case of *old reference*, new functionality is added to an old, out-of-use product. The general usage of the artifact is clear, as the artifact already familiar. The usage fits within users' mind-set and due to the original device it can add a nostalgic or romantic vintage feeling to the product.

A *secret language* makes the "conversation" more engaging. Certain devices enable a new language between the users on a rudimentary level some allow complex coding. However, these intimate and confidential messages are not explicit as in "virtual sex". Communicating in a way that is open for interpretations results in more freedom for creating meanings in an *abstract way*.

X-series

After selecting the most promising attributes based on previous research, a series of concepts was developed (Figure 2 – 7) to evoke a wide range of relatedness communication experiences, called the X-series.

The concepts were derived through a Design Inclusive Research (Horvath, 2007) process where experiences were tested through iterations. The combination of attributes that were embedded within the products were tweaked and adjusted to strengthen the NVC experiences, to become crystalized and to be expressed in a successful combination. People in *LDRs* and design experts expressed their feelings and opinions on the six prototypes as part of the verification. Figures 2-7 show the X-series concepts and their attributes.

Lempi

Lempi means favorite, love, and fondness in Finnish language. The product Lempi derives from one of the X-series' products, Xplore, that communicates location and memories.

Lempi makes you dare to deal with your long-distance relationship. It challenges the situation of being apart and may even emphasize this separation. However, Lempi also gives positive insights on locations. The issue with long-distance is not only the physical separation but also the mental separation: one usually does not know what the other one is experiencing today, the partners do not know the favorite places of each other, one does not have mutual everyday experiences to talk about.

Lempi enables storytelling by reporting about location-related experiences and emotions (*intimate mobile*), and thus links partners' daily life (*daily routines*). Lempi aims to create content between the partners in their remote environments and thus build a bridge across the distance (*closer*). One can tag (*logging*) memorable and hopeful locations (uncertainty reduction theory) that are linked to the couple. The other way round, the user gets *unobtrusive*

Figure 9. Attributes embedded within Lempi.

Figure 10. Lempi user instructions (to see Lempi in action https://youtu.be/_bLLhfYo56g).

Day 1

date:

Store one important location

- Pull the bottom out while holding the pointer up.
- Value your mood matching the location by turning the bottom clockwise.
- Push in the bottom to store the location.

Why did you choose this location?

Why did you give it this value?

Which other locations would you like to store? And why?

What are your first thoughts / impressions on Lempi concept?

Where do you store Lempi?
when at home:

when on the road:

How often do you think about Lempi?

How often do you come across Lempi?

Problems regarding the usage?

Figure 11. Diary, day 1 task and questions.

color-coded notifications, surprises (*surprise effect*) and gets more familiar with the partner's daily life. Lempi can lead to interesting conversations and questions to know each other better, resulting in more engaging and meaningful communication. Lempi is also a companion that helps the user to feel safe and comforts when being stressed or missing the partner. It takes the users to those places where they feel close (*hedonic quality*). In addition, via Lempi the partners can give each other tips and recommendations about the locations in their environment. Lempi guides the user to these locations when nearby next time (*different sense*).

Lempi is small, round, simple and ambiguous (*abstract*). The build of it is robust and reliable. The aesthetics of form already evokes emotions: the compass-shape follows the idea to an *old reference*. The *rich interaction* is implemented in its simple handling; each action mode requires a different orientation of the product towards the user. Unlike with an application on a laptop or a phone, one can touch and feel Lempi as a separate sacred and *personal device*.

The meaningful content of the stories is stored within the product, waiting to be re-experienced (*tangibility*) later on when *LDRs* meet in person, to make those moments even richer.

Methodology

Phenomenological method

The goal of this study is to design for experiences and thus the study uses a phenomenological research method. As Fokkinga & Desmet (2012, p.3-4) suggest, there are certain conditions that allow the participants share their experiences, stories and opinions openly: There should be no prejudice and the researcher should be equally interested in each topic touched upon by the participants

A diary study was chosen as a qualitative research method to simulate how the product would fit into users' daily lives and to get feedback on their emotions during this study. The aim is to achieve subjective perceptions, as these triggered *NVC* experiences and the stories they are embedded in cannot be achieved otherwise.

A diary study is a quick and inexpensive way of obtaining real-world data about peoples' behavior and experiences. The researcher gets the opportunity to witness subtle behavior as the participant can note activities they may not otherwise recall in a typical research interview. In addition, the diary study is followed by an in-depth interview to give more insight into their past experiences.

Sample

Four couples from different types of *LDRs* were recruited. They were selected based on different parameters such as how much time and distance they are apart. Two couples live in the same country but had different schedules, seeing each other only during weekends, while the other two meet less often than once a month, showcasing more extreme *LDRs*.

The participants were between 20 and 35 years old. Born between 1980-1995, they have grown up with the rapidly advancing technology within *ICT*, Internet and mobile computing. Thus, they are adapted to different *CMC* technologies such as Skype, email and Facebook to connect.

A non-probabilistic judgmental sample method was used. The population was contacted through social media channels, which also functions as sampling criteria: The participants need to have adapted to some social media to be able to show some adaptation to Lempi as well. The sample is non-representative and limited in size. However, for the purposes of this study, the sample size and the sampling method were considered sufficient.

store

Storing one location

Go to the location/environment you want to store.

Pull the bottom out while holding Lempi vertical with the pointer up.

Value your experience matching the location by turning the bottom clockwise. You can do this according to the colour or to the amount of the LEDs that light up.

Push in the bottom to store the location. The LED ring turns off now

As this is a simulation, please check-in at this location via foursquare as well

Figure 12. Manual.

Diary study

In the diary study participants reflect on their communication behavior and experiences for seven days. The study was done using *Foursquare application* (now *Swarm*, by *Foursquare*) as the fully-functional prototypes were not available at the time due to problems with programming the prototype. *Foursquare*, a social media application for location sharing, provided a suitable solution for the diary study. The participants were instructed to use the application with a new account connected only with their partner, simulating the use of *Lempi*. For instance, when checking in to a location they were asked to write a number or color, related to the location, with notifications turned on for *Foursquare*. The mock-up experiment with *Foursquare* had certain downsides, such as the message being written, instead of using color-coded lights. In addition, *Foursquare* is an application embedded within a phone, not a separate device. For the study, the users were given a non-functional prototype of *Lempi* that looks like a finished product but does not function.

The use of the diary was first explained with a short survey. The study includes response scales that are used in varying ways as the users have different perceptions. However, scales are compared only within one participant's answers (MacKerron, 2011). The daily assignments in the diary stimulate the use of *Lempi* in all its aspects, storing and revisiting experiential, meaningful and memorable locations. At the end, there was a survey for the participants to reflect on the past experiences.

The participants got a manual explaining the simulation through *Foursquare*. The exact interaction of *Lempi* was explained in detail to ensure that participants got the best possible idea of *Lempi* during the simulation.

Interview

The in-depth interview clarified beliefs, argumentations, vision, opinions, behavior and experiences with a focus on the couple. The interview was semi-structured, enabling analyzing the patterns of the different diaries. The participants were interviewed in person or via Skype.

First, the participants were asked to reflect on how *Lempi* works to know how the participants interpret and understand *Lempi*. For a more structured view, the participant chose 5 cards best describing the experience and 5 that are not related at all out of a 50-carddeck (Emotional response cards by Azeim, 2012).

At the end, the other concepts from the X-series were presented and they were asked how they feel about those in comparison with *Lempi*.

Analysis

The diaries and interviews were summarized, formatted and coded in a thematic analysis, focusing on the words and expressions that helped evoke the NVC relatedness experiences. Through an analysis of the experiences described by the participants, the most important attributes were abstracted.

Results

Response

The 8 participants completed 52 daily assignments in total. There were differences between the participants and the relatedness experiences evoked, as well as regarding the reflections on NVC. All of them used various types of CMC to communicate on a daily basis. Their decisions on using these channels were based on cost and ease of use and less on the evoked relatedness experiences. They were adapted to CMC

such as leaving *Skype* on while they were working.

Acceptance of the prototype

The first impressions varied significantly, which resulted in different ways of accepting Lemp: Some reflected on the usage of the item and even question the use, value, technology or existence of Lemp. An application and faster interaction would be more justified. Consequently using Lemp required more attention from them, as they were confused about the communication that Lemp facilitates.

Others reflected on the meaning, seeing Lemp as romantic and theatrical. They expected a 90's mobile phone but got something entirely different. Consequently, they keep Lemp exposed. They show their friends what they got and tell them they like it. One participant got a comment from a friend "I almost hoped I was in a long-distance relationship so I could try this!"

The other X-series concepts were seen as more futuristic solutions. They give answers to questions participants did not even ask themselves. They feel that Lemp understands their need: the craving for different ways to express themselves. The interview proved the participants have a fair to good understanding of how Lemp would function.

After seeing the multiple possibilities of NVC in the X-series' scenarios all participants wanted to have their own communication customized, primarily by adding different channels to the communication. The wishes included physical contact, multi-colored messages, communicating more activities at once, or sound recordings connected to a certain location, in order to know each other's environment better.

One participant came up with the idea to take a picture and share how beautiful a place was at that certain moment. *Visual messages* seemed tempting for many participants, as it enables capturing experiences on the spot from their perspective.

Some would justify the usage of Lemp if it could function as a *logbook* and give an on-demand overview. *Logging* allows Lemp to be an ideal tracker for trips. Both partners have more freedom though capture the experience on the right moment. They could document the journey and reports are sent when connection is available. Also as a holiday planner Lemp helps to organize and remember places where people want to go together.

Relatedness Experiences

For some participants Lemp did not make them feel like being part of each other's life by reporting on their own activities, though they did feel so when getting more insight into their partner's daily activities. They wanted to get recommendations for locations from each other. Locations as such are not experienced as meaningful and instead they felt being monitored.

Others felt strongly emotionally connected. Receiving messages is perceived as valuable because the notifications make them feel that they are thinking of

each other. This more concrete emotional connection is also expressed by *re-experiencing* certain moments in *tangible* places. There is an increased interest in each other when storing and receiving locations. Lemp is seen as an empathic friend that can pass your feelings to your partner. Lemp will never be anything *obtrusive* as they recognize other tools for urgent matters, such as a phone call or sending a text message.

Finally some participants felt having Lemp *mobile* helps already to feel close, and forgetting Lemp would be the same as leaving behind their partner as it embodies and connects them. As long as Lemp is with their partner they will be notified through this medium, the other one will be all right in Lemp's company. They see Lemp as a *personal device*, carefully crafted and selected only for them. When they do not visit enough locations a feeling of guilt emerges, as *equity* is lost. Lemp *supports* them in being apart.

Usage

Mainly due to busy schedules participants went to look for special or pleasant activities within their *daily routine*. However, they did not want to report about work, as they do not want their work life to be involved in their intimate communication. It seemed sufficiently satisfying to just *surprise* each other with the activity or the location that the other one does not know about. This creates more interest, which can contribute a conversation as they start wondering what is meaningful about that location. The behavioral change can be seen as nonverbally enriched, as more mutual curiosity is generated.

When some participants are together over the weekend they store a *shared experience* together at a party they attend, to *memorize* for later.

Some participants store locations that have to do with an upcoming change in their life. They look for *future plans* in their environment next to their daily activities. One couple had ideas of going to certain locations, preferably together.

Another couple stored beloved locations as both partners could *escape* from their daily rush to be in some place where they feel at peace and related.

Meanings

The notification in itself is already a message as the participants saw what their partner felt when receiving the message. These color-coded messages made possible many meanings that only the partners understood. This *abstract* form also helped expression in different ways; Lemp gives more information by only location and an amount of LEDs. Every couple generated their own *secret language* through Lemp as the couples adapted to using Lemp.

By linking *mood* to a location, participants got empathic about each other's day-to-day live. For instance, they did not know how valued some places were to the other one. A certain mood could be communicated more straightforward in a pure way,

without being biased by the communication channel. Lempi has also worked as a part of a show-off game: They tell how well they are doing and how great the experiences are even without the partner. This way Lempi can turn into a competition. However, it can also feel like being monitored or getting jealous.

Some put more stress on the *activity* than on the location. For instance, they tell in different shades of red how well they ate at a restaurant. In their coding, each color stands for a different activity, with varying intensity. They adapted their communication and gave it meaning in their own way.

The feeling of getting closer was even perceived in different ways. Communicating the *distance* makes the time spend together more meaningful as they are separated from each other. Lempi is comforting and supportive. As the device itself already evokes the feeling of care and comfort, it can link this feeling to certain places. The *old reference* to a compass makes the concept clear and easier to adapt to the *guidance*.

The story told through the product is of great importance and it can increase the functionality of Lempi, even though just the product as such has meaning. When the concept of Lempi was further explained at the end of the interview, the prototype was perceived even better and the participants felt more understood by Lempi. The *old reference* made Lempi familiar and everyone has used an item that resembles Lempi, which does not mean they are still using it. It helps building the relatedness experience, as there are expectations how the product should be used. One couple perceived Lempi and its form accessible. Participants enjoyed the *rich interaction* of Lempi by turning its control, as it has a round shape, even though it does not function at all.

Transformations in behavior

Lempi is challenging as it gets in the way, one has to think of an extra item and take it along. This way Lempi was used as a reminder for the unwanted behavior of forgetting things. Lempi is a slightly less able and naïve product that has the *hedonic quality* for good and wanted habits such as pursuing a healthy lifestyle by going to the gym.

The role of distance is frustrating and creates a *friction* between being together and apart. With Lempi the content of the connection is the distance, the exact thing that prevents them from seeing each other when they need mutual support the most. This way Lempi underlines how important it is to be together. Lempi is difficult, as it does not have diverse meanings at once, compared to the other available media. Lempi feels like slowing them down.

This way, Lempi makes them stop during the daily rush and take time for a Zen-moment to reflect on the relationship and being a couple. A peaceful spot is preferred to escape mentally to the seaside, being immersed in the environment that is open, quiet and beautiful. Another participant teleports mentally to his partner, making him feel physically closer. For many, Lempi is seen as a companion that needs to be

taken care of.

Lempi stimulates a *different sense* for many participants, the sense of place and direction (Jacobs, J., et al., 2013), by making them aware of their relationship spatially. Participants discovered that their environment is full of meaningful places, unfamiliar to the other one, when they are confronted by the specific previous experience in that location. One participant wanted more of these meaningful locations around her to create a network to feel close to her partner or storing objects, such as a car and sofa, location seen as *safe locations*.

Discussion

According to the results, attributes vary in their ability to evoke NVC relatedness experiences and the ones with the strongest impact are shown in Figure 13. For instance, notifications need to be of an *unobtrusive* kind. When a partner is notified the meaning, linked to a certain location in Lempi's case, is already communicated. Users can decide whether to check it immediately or later. Acceptance of notifications varies and acknowledging the differences can help to understand the partner's communication preferences. Using *secret language* showed interesting adaptation to Lempi and highlighted how a couple became intimate through Lempi.

Addressing a *different sense* is intriguing because it makes people aware that they have the ability to communicate and perceive in a different way. By using Lempi a sense of place, direction and orientation is addressed, making the participants more aware of their environment. In addition, the usage of locations confronted the participants with each other. They did not know that some places had so much meaning for the other.

As in the case of Lempi, it is beneficial to not focus on screens, as they are already omnipresent. Screens are useful for sending explicit information, but also hard to use and demand very direct information. Contrary to that, the core idea is to leave some openness for interpretation, to allow ambiguity. One could argue that Lempi is too ambiguous for an aesthetical interaction but it was built as an open and unique platform for partners to facilitate and research expressivity. The interaction was the medium to achieve the experience. The interaction should not take the forefront compared to the experience one gets from the communication with the partner. The focus is not on the interaction with the product itself.

The method used includes problems. For instance, all participants were in a similar stage, not married nor with children. Their future perspectives were alike: within a month they were united again, at least for some time. This could have lead to the perception they were about to end their *LDR*, with better times were ahead. Due to such parameters and with the non-probabilistic judgmental sample used, the results are not to be generalized. Nevertheless, the results can help to understand other *LDRs* as well as NVC relatedness experiences.

Figure 13. The attributes with the most potential to evoke NVC relatedness experiences.

All participants knew the researcher, which eased talking about personal matters in a relaxed atmosphere but could be a source of bias. The participants were asked to be honest, critical and to express their doubts. A longer study would provide more knowledge, but will be more fruitful only when the prototype is fully functional and a more critical reflection on the embedded experiences is done (Hassenzahl et al., 2012).

Implications for future research and designs

To develop new NVC experiences, it needs to be taken into account that people have diverse preferences and by only providing one option of communication many people will drop out. Thus a product service system is desirable, starting from a basic product that can be extended over time, as both partners get to know their NVC capabilities better.

Location matters within LDRs and thus further research could deal with how places evolve along with the relationship, how they got their meaning and how this meaning fades or grows fonder. There are also other promising ways of addressing different senses, such as through scent, airflow and taste. Gesture technology such as kinetic tools or wristbands could help to develop this further.

The interaction should be recognizable so that the CMC channel does not evoke frustrations towards the technology itself and being unintentionally reflected on their partner. It also helps to make it attractive and acceptable. This is mainly the first step towards liking the product but also continues further on during the use of the product itself.

Conclusions

This study focuses on the ways a location can create

meaning, and hence not on the meaning a location has in a relationship. The chosen locations are meaningful, contributing to knowing each other better. Locations motivate questions leading to a conversation. The necessity of verbal communication is a positive consequence, not a drawback. It is beneficial because partners have more interest in each other, willing to know more. On a daily basis it is engaging to tell about yourself and make your partner aware of your experiences and stories. In addition, it contributes to future planning setting the scene for the next meet-up.

Attributes should not be haphazardly implemented; they need to be embedded within a story with a significant role in it. An imbalance between the story and the attributes results in weaker Relatedness Experiences. A next step could be more advanced storytelling practices.

People are not products you get intimate with by pressing a button or turning a switch. New meaningful interactions need to be explored and used instead of widely used existing product related interactions. New ways of NVC are interesting but sometimes artificial. They are less culturally influenced and do not try to imitate the real contact, done by using different terms such as orientation, direction and length of the NVC. There is no urge for simulation of the reality, but rather for new and subtler ways of meaningful connection.

Simulations are seen to replace real life meetings, and thus the product becomes a replacement of the real person and meetings would feel the same as the separation. New ways of nonverbal communication are sought so that the separation gives new experiences that are not possible while being together.

“Many authors appear to be aware of this difficulty (the lag that comes with technology) and therefore suggest a symbolic or poetic interpretation, rather than a one-to-one representation of physical intimacy, that is to replace physicalness with expressivity” (Hassenzahl et al., 2012, p 30:9)

Prototyping, such as with Lempi in this study, helps to find meaningful stories in research. Certain elements of Lempi can be used for future storytelling design. With Lempi the meaning is created by real life experiences. Nevertheless, you have to experience the story first to be able to relive the meaning.

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What is an ugly car? A grounded theory approach on a webpage's comments

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Abstract In automotive design, the misuse of some aesthetic variables such as proportion, symmetry or balances etc. during the aesthetic design process can produce a negative aesthetic response to the user such as, when people assess a car as ugly. However, there is not a systematic study about the elements which actually affect the aesthetics of a car and not even theories to aid the car's designers in this process. Thus, we applied a Grounded Theory methodology using as data source a Yahoo blog "10 ugliest cars of all time" to obtain a first approach about how people understand and perceive ugliness in a car. We found five hypotheses about how people make an aesthetic assessment of vehicles, which were faced with the aesthetic theories to confirm the results obtained.

Keywords Car, Ugliness, Grounded theory, Aesthetics, Design

Introduction

During a production run of four years the Pontiac Aztek, see Figure 1, commonly "derided as ugly", only sold 108,500 units; it was a huge flop for Pontiac Aztek (Elliott, 2010). Comments about its aesthetics were merciless:

"The Aztek is the only car that I can remember that people would walk by and actually point and laugh at you when you were driving it, (...) people would giggle and point because it was so hideous looking." (Jake Fisher, Consumer Reports).

Let us consider two fundamental assumptions for this paper based on common knowledge: the first on ugly as an aesthetic assessment and the second on the opposition beauty-ugliness.

First assumption: ugly as an Aesthetic Assessment (AEA)

When we make an AEA, of something, "ugly" is a possible result. AEA in product and automotive design is very important because it allows companies to design more competitive products with aesthetics geared to a population segment of consumers; the attention of the users is attracted by good aesthetics which fills their needs and fulfill their most important values and aspirations (da Silva et al 2013; Dell'Era, Verganti 2007; Crilly et al. 2004; Crilly et al 2009, Crilly, 2010). Chinese producers are the largest manufacturers in the world by the number of cars produced each year. Their aesthetic design is improving every year. Consequently, people's AEA on vehicles of Western carmakers will be even more demanding in the future.

We make many AEA through our daily lives; however little is known scientifically about how we make them (Kozbelt & Kauffman, 2015). Our daily experience shows us that we make those assessments in a rather automatic and effortless way: they may result in quickly and spontaneously our (aesthetic) opinions on

Figure 1. Pontiac Aztek: an industrial flop due to its ugliness? But, what makes a car ugly? Photo: IFCAR [Public domain], via Wikimedia Commons

a certain matter. As psychological aesthetic constructs, they are affected by a lack of reliability: there is a disagreement between individuals when assessing an aesthetic artifact and the replication of results may be poor across multiple types of researches (Tinio & Smith, 2014). Also on the validity: when we say that something is "beautiful" or "ugly", what are we precisely evaluating in a product? A part of a product? The whole product? (Goodman, 1968) argued that artworks possess relatedness, and we believe that cars do too. This feature means that any particular aspect of them (color, contrast, delicate brush strokes) can be very relevant for the aesthetic experience.

Carrying out an aesthetic assessment in research one or many subjective or objective aspects can be measured (Kozbelt & Kauffman, 2015). Five subjective constructs are currently (Kozbelt & Kauffman, 2015): aesthetic sentiment, aesthetic experience, aesthetic judgment, aesthetic preference, and aesthetic pleasure. Two of the objective aspects considered are the indices of aesthetic achievement and, the characteristics of the artifact (i.e., Gestalt properties). Many other measurements are possible as well. For a review (Kozbelt & Kauffman, 2015). The question resulting from AEA is: Which are the terms or concepts related to AEAs on ugly cars?

Second assumption: the opposition ugliness-beauty

The second assumption is that we tend to use “ugliness” as a term opposed to “beauty”. However, one question that needs to be asked is: is ugliness the opposite of beauty? Or, is it a term opposed to something else? Could a theoretical overview of ugliness be able to answer this question? Therefore, we will present a theoretical overview of ugliness to examine existing accounts to resolve this question.

Historically, beauty has been one of the main concerns of aesthetics. The lack of an ugliness theory is noticeable. Many different approaches on ugliness have been developed through history. For instance, for Plato and Aristotle ugliness was simply the opposite of beauty. This powerful idea dominated aesthetics until the beginning of the 20th century: ugliness was something without an aesthetic value (Kuplen, 2013). In the “Aesthetic of ugliness” Rosenkrantz, (1853), described ugliness as an analogy with moral evil, this being the opposite of the good.

In line with seeing ugliness as the opposite to beauty, Eco (2007) compares the synonyms of beautiful (pretty, cute, pleasing attractive ...etc.) and ugly (repellent, horrible, horrendous, disgusting...etc.) to conclude that “whereas all the synonyms for beautiful could be conceived as a reaction of disinterested appreciation, almost all the synonyms for ugly contain a reaction of disgust, if not of violent repulsion, horror, or fear”. Hillman (1981) argues that the ugly creates more strong aesthetic responses than the beautiful. Hagman (2011) argues that ugliness is the traumatic disruption of an aesthetic experience; the formal qualities of the object turn out to be the origin “of the most repulsive and disgusting feelings”. P 7.

In psychological aesthetics, little is known of what ugliness constitutes. There are no consensual responses to two main questions: Is beautiful the opposite to ugly? Are ugliness and beauty opposed constructs? Stich (2004) suggests that beauty and ugliness are not two opposed poles along the same dimension but are “two independent dimensions”. According to her, aesthetic-affective responses consist of two orthogonal dimensions representing the response to ugly and beautiful objects. On the other hand, society and culture affect ugliness as well, for example, elegance and sophistication have been associated with higher classes, contrary to the lower ones where ugliness would be more common.

The diversity of concepts shown above, and the lack of theoretical links among them, shows an important gap in the field of the aesthetics of the ugly. Moreover, the absence of experimental or systematic observational works in this overview supports the view of the lack of an ugliness theory constructed on empirical grounds which makes it difficult to try to study the subject systematically. In conclusion, it is not clear if ugliness is the opposite of beauty or if it is a term opposed to something else.

The data: the webpage comments

The 10 ugliest cars ranking

In this paper, we are interested in how real people use the ugly term in their everyday life because we think that it is a first step understanding ugliness. An approach studying this would be studying people in their daily lives; however this is highly time-consuming. Incidentally, we came across a huge source of data concerning people’s comments about ugly cars made by the visitors of the Yahoo blog The 10 ugliest cars of all time, which in the last review on 05 November 2015 it contained 3968 comments. The list of the cars was created by Karl Brauer who has been in the automotive publishing industry for 20 years as CEO and editor in chief of TotalCarScore.com and Edmunds.com. The list is shown in Table 1, which includes similar rankings from other web-pages. Almost all the cars presented in those web-pages are from 1945 onwards. (Huffman, 2013) advances one reason for this:

“ (...) to 21st century eyes it’s tough to make judgments in the context of 75 or 85 years ago. And before that, the way a car looked was almost always determined solely by how its primitive parts bolted together. Design virtually didn’t exist.”

The cars presented are from any domestic car category: sedans, SUVs, MPVs, compacts, etc. We believe that this increases the difficulty of the ranking task because different cars categories possess very different appearances, i.e., it would be easier to compare an SUV with an SUV than to compare an SUV with a sedan. We believe that this compromises the validity and reliability of those rankings. Table 1 shows a highly noticeable lack of coincidences among the rankings. The Pontiac Aztek is the most frequent car in the table (6 times), followed by the AMC Gremlin (1970-1978), 4 times, and the Fiat Multipla 1998 with 3 times. However, as a mitigating factor, it should be considered that the number of car models in the time period considered is over thousands. The ranking refers to a model of one specific year or for a time period between some years.

Characteristics of 10Ugliest blog comments

The blog allows posting comments (“posts”) by the page visitors. The comments are the opinions and thoughts of the visitors to the page; they are chronologically arranged (Jansen, 2008). The language used in these comments is considered less structured, more ambiguous and harder to understand than in well-formed texts (Jansen, 2008). The interaction among the page’s users, for instance, feedback through thumbs up or down icon, was not considered.

All of the comments contained in the blog are a rich and free source of readily available data focused on the subject of the ugly car. However, in this case, we cannot ensure that all comments are serious opinions or thoughts. It is clear that some of them are funny or made for teasing.

This blog was chosen because it allows the posting of unrestricted spontaneous or thoughtful comments by

the visitors, who do not have, necessarily, knowledge of cars, assuring that any person can comment. However, probably, amateurs on cars or other opinion leaders on car styling could post comments about the subject too.

The research problem depends on how to take advantage of this low structured data to find out some determinants of the ugliness of a car. We believe that a multifaceted problem such as ugliness requires an exploratory and open-ended method approach capable of identifying its components, even if they are of different levels. Moreover, to tackle this problem systematically, the research objectives must cover the individual, the artifact and the context where the aesthetic interaction is carried out. Thus, the main question of this paper is: which concepts or terms are related to the ugly and ugliness comments on cars? And how are those concepts related?

Hence, the research objective is to identify new-concepts and categories making up probable determinants of ugliness and to develop hypothesis and insights worthy of being researched systematically further. This is why we used a grounded theory approach.

The remaining of this paper is structured as follows: In section 2, the method and the used procedure are described. In section 3 the results of the analysis are presented in tables containing the categories and examples obtained from the comments. Finally, in the point 3.F, some hypotheses were formulated which are discussed in section 4.

Method

The grounded theory approach: its conceptual basis

Grounded Theory (GT) is an inductive general research methodology (Glaser & Strauss, 1967) which is based on data collected in the words and actions of those

individuals under study (Goulding, et al. 2005) p 29. The theory may thus be generated initially from the data and it evolves along the research through interplay of data collection and analysis (Strauss & Corbin, 1994). Instead of an exhaustive literature review of ugliness before entering into the field, the developing theory makes the researcher focus on relevant literature, where the grounded concepts emerge (Goulding, et al. 2005). However, GT would be specially adapted to address ugliness if we consider the fact that aesthetic literature on ugliness is rare and even rarer in product design.

A misconception of GT is that the researcher should go into the field not knowing of any theory related to the phenomenon, though; this would favor that the theory emerges essentially from the data (Goulding, et al. 2005). Nevertheless, what is required is that the core categories emerge in a delicate balance between drawing on the researcher's reading and life experiences while keeping an open mind about the concepts emerging from the data (Goulding, et al. 2005).

The GT was chosen for this study because; first it allows the creation of theoretical categories from the review of poorly structured data, such our case, in a systematic, agile and flexible way. Second, it allows research on the world of real users which is not biased by any experimental conditions or requirements, and this without a preconceived hypothesis (Glaser & Strauss, 1971). In other words, it would allow the formulation of a clear hypothesis in order to understand the reasons of why a person considers a car as ugly. Third, concerning the data source, in GT the researchers must look for events in a representative community of the phenomenon and the interactions where the phenomenon is expressed. One must look for the people who are most likely to provide pertinent information (Goulding, et al., 2005). This is exactly the case of a specialized internet page with comments, which is accepted as a common source of data in GT (Strauss & Corbin, 1994).

Table 1. Ranking ugliest cars.

	10 Ugliest Cars of All Time - CNBC.com/ Yahoo! Cars	The World's Ugliest Cars. Bloomberg Businessweek	Top 10 Ugliest Cars Ever - RM AutoBuzz	10 of the world's ugliest cars - Telegraph	100 Ugliest Cars of All Time Edmunds.com
1	Mercury Zephyr 1978	Chevrolet Chevette	Porsche Panamera 2010-present	Jeep Cherokee 2014	Lamborghini Veneno 2014
2	Edsel Corsair 1958	Ford Edsel	Ford Granada 1975-1980	Pontiac Aztek 2001-2005	Lincoln Versailles 1977
3	Pontiac Trans Sport 1990	AMC Matador	Ford Fairlane 1957-1959	Yaris Verso	Acura ZDX 2010
4	Aston Martin Lagonda 1982	Chevrolet Corvair	Nissan Cube 2009-2014	Fiat Multipla	Cadillac Deville 1985
5	AMC Marlin 1965	AMC Gremlin	Hyundai Tiburon 2000-2001	Subaru Impreza 2000	Pontiac Aztek 2001
6	Pontiac Aztek 2001	Chevrolet Vega	Chevrolet Malibu Maxx 2004-2007	Mini Cooper Paceman	Fiat Multipla 1998
7	Plymouth Valiant 1960	Pontiac Aztek	AMC Gremlin 1970-1978	Ford Scorpio	Datsun F10 1974
8	Isuzu VehiCross 1999	Ford Pinto	Lincoln Continental Mark VI 1980 - 1981	SsangYong Rodius	Edsel 1958
9	Isuzu Axiom 2002	Yugo	Pontiac Aztek 2001 - 2005	BMW X6	Bristol Blenheim 1976
10	AMC Gremlin 1970	AMC Pacer	Davis D-2 Divan 1948	Subaru Tribeca	BMW 7 Series 2002

Figure 2. GT process.

Procedure

The technique of theory generation was applied from textual data (Strauss & Corbin, 1994). Firstly, Data collection should be coded according to an established family of codes, then the coding data is organized into categories named Core Categories, secondly the data is re-categorized to obtain more accurate information, into a second level of categories called category 2.0, with the objective to find concepts that would be Thirdly, where the information comes from, in GT the researchers must look for events in a representative community of the phenomenon and the interactions where the phenomenon is expressed, see Figure 2. One must look for the people who are most likely to provide pertinent information (Goulding, et al, 2005). This is exactly the case of the comments on a specialized internet page, which is accepted as a common source of data in GT (Strauss & Corbin, 1994) the basis for some Theoretical Reflections, which lead to a final hypothesis.

In GT once the researcher starts codifying the data, the codes are used to look for the presence of data belonging to those codes iteratively. There is a continuous interplay between data and codification. The result of the adapted methodology is a convergent-divergent process where the data is constantly compared iteratively, allowing to obtain information to finally formulate the theory.

A — Data

The data must be collected from the original sources using the original language and expressions of the people, without any alteration.

B — Family Code

This stage starts by assigning codes for the raw data using Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software. Each comment of the text must be taken, line by line, and named according to some *families codes* previously defined. (These are defined by the researcher)

C — Core Category

Once all the comments are clustered in *family codes*, it is necessary to compare the codes according to perceived similar patterns, a higher level of abstraction; these categories are then grouped into

Figure 3. Detailed GT process.

more precise categories which finally make up the *core categories*.

D — Category 2.0

When the *core categories* are established and the first categorization is made a second categorization is made by similarity with the topics of the first categorization until a saturation point is reached, i.e., when the researcher does not find further new information or elements.

E — Concepts

The comments contained in the *categorization 2.0* should be analyzed this building concepts that meet the main ideas (Pre-hypothesis), which later will allow doing theoretical reflections.

F — Theoretical reflections

At this point, hypotheses are formulated according to the *core categories* and the thoughts about the concepts obtained in the previous point.

Results

The method used here will be explained in detail point by point below. See Figure 3.

A — Data recollection

The data was collected from the comments of 10Ugliest blog webpage, where people gave their opinion about the list of the 10 ugliest cars presented by the webpage’s author. There were 6039 comments in 539 pages.

B — Family Code

The analysis starts by assigning codes for the raw data used. Each comment of the text was taken, line by line, and codified according to the *family codes* that we defined before to start the review of the comments (Brand car’s, Aesthetic appreciation and Extra qualities) see *Table 2. Family Code*. The codification was made until reaching a saturation point.

C — Core Category

Once the comments were encoded into the three family codes. We made a new categorization based on comments patrons of the topics contained in those

family codes such as, aesthetics, emotions, memories, functionality and semantic symbols see Figure 5. This led us to arrive at two core categories which covered and enclosed the main topics of the new categories: (i) User Experience (UX) which is constituted for three levels, aesthetic, meaning and emotional, make up the user experience (Hekkert & Schifferstein 2008). The aesthetic level is associated with the “product’s capacity to delight one or more of our sensory modalities” (Hekkert & Leder 2008). The emotional experiences, are those “typically considered in emotion psychology and in everyday language about emotions, such love or anger, which are elicited by the appraised relational meaning of products” (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007) and the meaning level is “the ability to assign personality or other expressive characteristics and to assess the personal or symbolic significance of products”. , (ii) Functionality, it is related to the performance of vehicles. Some examples of the new categorization and the comments contained there are shown in *Table 3. Core Category*.

Table 2. Family Code.

Family code	Explanation	Example
Amc Gremlin, Aston Martin Lagonda, Edsel Corsair, Isuzu Axiom, Isuzu Vehicross, Mercury Zephyr, Pontiac Aztek, Pontiac Trans sport, Pymouth Valiant, Amc Marlin.	codes refer to the brand of the car mentioned	Comment: “the Marlin was already outdated, too big, and AMC was a brand with a reputation for mechanical failings. By then, only self-abusers or the clueless would buy AMC”. Code: AMC Marlin
Aesthetic appreciation: Beautiful, Ugly	This category was determined according to the perceived appreciation (positive or negative) of each comment	Comment: “I think the AMC Marlin is a sweet looking ride. Throw a nice paint job and some wicked rims. PERFECT!!!” Code: Beautiful Comment: “Also rather than the Valient, I would have certainly considered the ugliness of extreme boredom that was the visual design of the Aspen” Code: Ugly
Extra qualities	Refers to non-aesthetic qualities.	Comment: “I loved my Gremlin. It was a great running car with good economy. A perfect second car” Code: Extra qualities

Table 3. Core Category.

Core Categories referring to UX, Aesthetic level: <i>Aesthetic, shape, color, positive perception, negative perception</i> .		
UX: Aesthetics	Explanation	Example
Negative perception	If a comment contain negative appreciations of cognitive nature.	“The Edsel was actually referred to as the “toilet seat” in its time due to the horrible shape of its grill”
Core Categories referring to UX, Semantic level: <i>Model, Semantic</i>		
UX: Semantic	Explanation	Example
Semantic	Semantic, symbols, values, expressive elements	“You say ugly, to some I say classic.”
Core Categories referring to UX, Emotion level: <i>Emotion</i>		
UX: Emotion	Explanation	Example
Emotion	Emotions, Feelings, moods	“I’m surprised the Nissan Cube isn’t on this list. Too bad Pontiac is gone though, my first car was a Pontiac Grand Am, and then I traded it for a Sunfire-best car I’ve had so far.”
Core Categories referring to Functionality		
Component	Any physical component or part of the car	“I bought a 1958 Edsel Corsair after college in 1968. Low mileage, excellent condition and very cheap price.”

D — Categories 2.0

After the first categorization in the previous point, a second categorization was made. This emerged after having analyzed the comments contained in the point of core categorization and was found to have similarities in some topics, which drove us to make a new categorization until the point of saturation. See *Table 4. Category 2.0*. Here we form more precise categories.

E — Concepts

Using the comments contained in the categorization 2.0, some concepts were deduced. These correspond to the main idea which explained a phenomenon enclosed in each of the categories see *Table 4. Concepts*. They are presented as Pre-hypothesis which later will allow the making of theoretical reflections. Some of them are shown below. See *Table 5. Concepts*.

F — Theoretical reflection

By using the Core categories which comprise the two main topics extracted from the categorization process (UX and Functionality), some hypotheses were formulated to answer our questions: Which terms or concepts are related to AEAs on ugly cars? And, how are they related? In an opposite way? These hypotheses are:

H1. There is a high attraction for classic, simple but unique and novel features in cars.

H2. People tend to make emotional assessments, based on previous experiences with cars.

H3. People make positive AEAs when cars have exaggerated shapes or uncommon colors but preserve certain characteristics of their time.

H4. People make negative AEAs when there is not a consistency in shapes, colors and quantity of elements of a vehicle, generating imbalance in their whole.

H5. People make positive AEAs if they have had good experiences with functional characteristics of the cars.

Discussion

Based on the GT results, we can highlight that for ordinary people (without specialized knowledge in automotive design or aesthetics) ugliness is not understood as the opposite of beauty as we postulated at the introduction. Conversely, we identified that people use the two levels of the UX, and functionality of the car, as base concepts to make an AEA, where aesthetics is seen just as a fraction of the ugly concept.

Table 4. Categories 2.0.

Core Categories referring to UX in categorization 2.0, Aesthetic Level:

Analogies to compare, Color attribute, Car's Shape, Aesthetic positive preference, Aesthetic negative preference, Styles

Categories 2.0	Explanation of the comments	Example
The shape of the cars	About the shape and materials of vehicle.	"How the Honda Element and that other squared looking car with small tyres"
Aesthetic negative Preference	People make negative aesthetic assessments of the vehicles.	"The ugliest car, is the Lincoln Navigator, or the Cadillac Escalade, Terrible design, horrible"

Core Categories referring to UX in categorization 2.0, Semantic Level: *Adjectives*

Categories 2.0	Explanation of the comments	Example
Adjectives	People using adjectives to do aesthetics assessment.	"I loved my Gremlin, It was sport, sexy and had tons of room in the hatchback"

Core Categories referring to UX in categorization 2.0, Emotion Level: *Emotion- feeling*

Categories 2.0	Explanation of the comments	Example
Emotion – feeling	Related with expressed memories about their cars or emotions that it evokes. I.e. related with their family, school, friends, youth and traveling.	"The gremlin, a car only the owner could love"

Core Categories Functionality: *Functional attribute*

Categories 2.0	Explanation of the comments	Example
Emotion	Emotions, Feelings, moods	"I'm surprised the Nissan Cube isn't on this list. Too bad Pontiac is gone though, my first car was a Pontiac Grand Am, and then I traded it for a Sunfire-best car I've had so far."

Core Categories referring to Functionality: *Functional attribute*

Categories 2.0	Explanation of the comments	Example
Functional attribute	Related to the operation of the vehicles.	"The Edsel, actually incorporated some ingenious innovations such as a headlight that tracked along with the steering, among other"

Table 5. Concepts.

UX-Category: Emotion and Memories	
Concept:	Example
People associate good memories with the function, quality, performance and durability of the vehicle.	"I loved my Gremlin. I was fun, fast and handled very well. I learned how to really "DRIVE" a car with my Gremlin. I learned how to do 360's on wet pavement and that saved me and my family years later by avoiding a serious accident. My kids thought I was a stunt driver. It cost \$ 2200.00, got 27 mile to the gallon and was reliable. Mine was a 72, before they started to ruin the styling. If you never have one, you can't really talk about them."
Having good memories of the vehicles does not ensure a positive aesthetic assessment.	"My best friend in high school had a Gremlin. We called it the high top sneaker. Places in the floor board were rusted out, so you had to watch where you put your feet. Ugly car, but it holds great memories. We laughed our butts off in that thing"
Aesthetic assessments of vehicles are part of people's memories	"Oh come on Yahoo, The Mercury Zephyr was my first car. How dare you call it Ugly!
People evaluating the vehicles, attribute sentiments as boring or love	"Y absolutely LOVED my Aztec"
UX-Category: Shape	
Concept:	Example
An AEA related with heavy and big looking shapes.	"The Marlin was already outdated, too big, and AMC was a brand with a reputation for mechanical failing. By then, only self-abusers or the clueless would buy AMC.
A negative assessment is related to not relating the different parts of the vehicles: bodywork and tyres size and interior and exterior of the car.	"How the Honda Element and that other squared looking car with small tires"
UX-Category: Analogies	
Concept:	Example
People use analogies to make negative aesthetic assessments. Using elements with a negative connotation to make reference to big shapes, weight, rectangle shapes, no fluent lines, size.	"The AMC pacer should have been on this list as it looked like an upside down fish bowl on wheels."
Negative analogies were used to evaluate the bodywork, lights and grill of the vehicle	"The edsel was actually referred to as the "toilet seat" in its time due to the horrible shape of its grill..."
Positive analogies were related to the functionalities over the aesthetic appearance of vehicles.	"They were real works horses, and practically indestructible"
People use analogies to make a negative AEA. Using elements with a negative connotation to make reference to big shapes, weight, rectangles shapes, no fluent lines, size.	"The AMC pacer should have been on this list as it looked like an upside down bowl on wheels"
UX-Category: Colour	
Concept:	Example
The colour in vehicles is an important aesthetic attribute to do a positive assessment but it is not a determinant.	"I thought the Matador looked pretty cool, if you got it with the right color schema."
People give attributes of cars by color paint. (I.e. sexy, classic, sporty)	"The Gremlin in the right color scheme with stripes was a sexy little car, which lended itself to customizing well, with a chopped top, it was WILD."
The color in vehicles is an important aesthetic attribute to make a positive assessment but it is not decisive for it.	"I thought the Matador looked pretty cool, if you got it with the right color schema"
UX-Category: Adjectives	
Concept:	Example
People use adjectives that are not related to the shape to make an aesthetic assessment as unique, classic, innovative, styling, simplistic, appealing.	"You say ugly, to some I say classic"
Negative assessment is related with the use of negative adjectives such as big, fat and grotesque.	"The Camaro on the other hand (which IS supposed to be beautiful) was beaten with an ugly stick several years ago. Fat, freaky, disproportionate, grotesque and more, why isn't IT ever attacked as being the truly ugly car it is???"

(part 1)

UX-Category: Style

Concept:	Example
Positive assessment is done by the style of the cars: Classic, exotic, sophisticated, futuristic, ahead of time.	"The Edsel was before its time. Ford should look at making a throwback/futuristic version. The grill, to me, is awesome."
Negative assessments are related with not adapted aesthetic tendencies.	"GM among others ruined a few models with the odd triangle shape redesigns in the 80's like the Olds Cutlass."

UX-Category: Positive aesthetic assessment

Concept:	Example
People generally do not use the word beauty to do aesthetics assessment.	"The Gremlin looked pretty good"
People do positive aesthetic assessment by using words: Cool, styling, pretty, awesome, sexy and spectacular.	"I think the Aston Martin Lagonda was one of the more spectacular cars ever constructed."

UX-Category: Negative aesthetic assessment

Concept:	Example
People use the word ugly to make negative AEA.	"If there is a definician for Butt ugly the AMC Pacer took first place."
People make comparisons between formal aspects of vehicles to make a negative aesthetic assessment.	"I can't believe the Chevy Aveo didn't make the list. That thing looks absolutely horrible. It's more painful than the Gremlin to look at."
The comfort and luxury in car designs affect the AEA.	"Most all of the automobiles since the advent of the first Ford Taurus have been super ugly, too damn small and uncomfortable"
People make AEA which is negative to current vehicles because designers do not include in the designs risky colors, textures and shapes, in the design.	"I prefer the old one's because time can change people's minds and what was outs of styles back then can be in style today. The newer "ugly" cars can't even make it 10 years without being nothing more than a melted ball of plastic"

Functionality-Category: Function

Concept:	Example
A positive assessment is related to the functionality of vehicles as performance, sound, power and fuel saving.	"Now, wait a minute. I bought a 1976 AMC Gremlin brand new and had it for seven years. Ran beautifully. The six-banger engine just kept going and going; never had a thing done to it in those seven years."
A negative assessment is associated with function of the stereo, transmission, power, quality, and buttons.	"The Falcon certainly needed to be on your Schidtyshst, as it was not only ugly, but also a mechanical Schidtboks, with bad engineering."

(part 2)

For example, from the UX semantic level, the AEAs performed by the participants of the web-page were related to symbolic values, associated with the trends and styles of each decade where there were shown to be a high attraction for classic, simple, unique and novel features. Also, people used analogies as a way to make negative assessments linking ugliness with objects or animals in a negative connotation, which according to Desmet & Hekkert, (2007) is a cognitive process used to "assess the personal or symbolic significance of products". We think that these assessments are the result of people's memories and a visceral response to characteristics of the product; this represents somehow a strong or light involvement with the product.

H2, on the emotional level, would reveal that people's appraisals are affected by previous experiences; those appraisals are expressed as love, pride, dislike or anger (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). These are unique for each participant of the web-page and refer to an emotional response to the experience they had with the cars, which were finally expressed in this case as negative or positive AEAs.

At the aesthetic level, we found that people make AEAs by referring to colors, shapes, quantity of formal elements and the existence of coherence between of car's visual characteristics as stated by H4. Also evident was a preference for vehicles which combine novel features as exaggerated shapes or uncommon colors but keep typical characteristics as expressed H1. This description corresponds to the MAYA principle, Most Advanced Yet Acceptable (Hekkert et al. 2003); (Jodard, 1992). This principle has been used in automotive design as a way to balance the amount of novelty and typicality present in a new car to finally gain the preference of customers (Diels et al., 2013): "the most successful cars have the MAYA principle in correct balance (...)", Bayley (2012), p. 12. However, when an imbalance is evident in some of the aesthetics characteristics of cars, as happened with some cars included in the list, the AEA is affected, resulting in an ugly car. Clough (2010) argues that car beauty is related to "clean, fluid lines and good proportion", p. 54, minimalist shapes and elegance and simplicity. He also confirms these findings, since he affirms that an imbalance between the novel, the innovative, and the typical gives rise to negative

appreciations. Thus, we believe that a poor control of aesthetic variables and standards of beauty (Hekkert, Leder, 2008) in car design, such as Golden ratio, balance, MAYA or peak shift (preference for an exaggerated color or shape in products) (Hekkert & Leder, 2008) might affect the aesthetic perception of the users producing finally a negative AEA as stated in H3.

Lastly, the functionality aspects of the vehicles such as performance and fuel economy also influenced the AEA, as expressed in H5. People's main expectations of a car would be about its correct functionality, rather than on aesthetics (Jordan 2002). These results satisfy Jordan's pyramid model and Kano's model (Matzler & Hinterhuber, 1998): products must work correctly and if this does not happen, people will be very disappointed with the product. So, in this case, people who had a good experience with functional characteristics of the cars made a positive AEA. Conversely, people with a bad functional experience made a negative AEA.

These findings finally, allow us to have an approach as to how people define what an ugly car is. We propose something that will call levels of ugliness which are formed for the aesthetic, emotional and meaning levels of UX, and the functionality. Results suggest that people cannot separate the ugly concept from those ugliness levels to make a negative AEA. That is why people use the word ugly when in at least one of the levels of ugliness, displeasure is generated (negative experiences).

The results and subsequent hypothesis generated are the beginning of a greater project: we will apply other methods to the Ugly Cars data to find out more response elements to the ugliness issue and to offer guidelines to car and product designers to avoid that problem.

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The Mary Poppins effect: Exploring a relationship between playfulness and creativity with the alternative uses test

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Abstract Prior research suggests there may be a relationship between play and creativity. In this study we focus on how the perception of playfulness of a creativity assessment relates to the performance on said creativity assessment. It is hypothesized that individuals who view an activity as play will be more creative than those that view that same activity as work. In this study, 106 professional engineers and scientists were given the alternative uses test (AUT). At the conclusion of the test, the participants were asked to subjectively rate the playfulness of that activity on a work-play scale of 1-5. Using quantity of ideas as an indicator of creative potential on the AUT, there was a strong positive correlation ($r^2=.94$) between creativity scores on the AUT and the playfulness ratings of the AUT. Specifically participants who viewed the activity as play (rating a 4 or 5) on average developed over twice as many ideas on the AUT than participants who viewed that activity as work (rating a 1). As data was available on number of patents awarded to each of these participants, we also found a moderate relationship between AUT scores and quantity of patents.

Keywords *Play, Creativity, Assessment, Patents, Alternative uses*

Introduction

As Mary Poppins begins the song "A Spoonful of Sugar" she expresses to the children that:

In every job that must be done
There is an element of fun
You find the fun and snap, the job's a game
And every task you undertake
Becomes a piece of cake

Mary is suggesting that when we view an activity as play we become more efficient at that activity. Although this is a fictional analogy, research suggests that there may be a link between play and creative performance. Creativity is a highly valued quality in industry. However, playfulness is not typically promoted or valued in an industry setting. This study suggests that people may be more creative in an activity if they view that activity as play as opposed to work. If this is true, it would support Poppins' logic, and more importantly, it would provide support for promoting playfulness in industry environments that value creativity.

Background

Creativity and play

"In Freud's psychodynamic theory, both play and creativity involve a high degree of unconscious primary process thinking" (Sawyer, 2012, p.71). Freud's theory was later developed by Russ, her contemporary version of Freud's theory states that "children and

adults who have 'controlled access to primary process thinking'- she called it affect-laden cognition- should be more creative thinkers" (as cited by Sawyer, 2012, p.71). In her study, Russ (1998) proposed a model that involved the cognitive and affective processes in creativity and highlighted the major connections between creativity and play. The connections as presented in her model are: divergent thinking, transformation abilities, expression of emotions, and expression of affect-laden fantasy (Russ, 1998). Many other studies emphasized the correlation between the quality and amount of pretend play with divergent thinking (Dansky & Silverman, 1973; Howard-Jones, Taylor, & Sutton, 2002; Moore & Russ, 2008; Russ & Schafer, 2006; Saracho, 1992). Johnson (1967) reported a strong correlation between social pretend play and both cognitive ability and divergent thinking; however, the isolated pretend play did not correlate with the same measures (as cited by Sawyer, 2012).

In a study conducted by Glynn (1994), she cued the same task as either 'work' or play' and observed if this changed students' behaviour toward the task. When participants were involved in the task cued as play, they were intrinsically motivated, violated the rules of the given task, and were more organic in their responses. However, when the participants were involved in the same task cued as work, they were more goal oriented, highly aware of their performance, and working hard to get more organized responses (Glynn, 1994). According to research, intrinsic motivation is extremely important in creativity

because it encourages an individual to continue on a task and persist on problem solving (Amabile, 1983; Prabhu, Sutton, & Sausser, 2008). Other researchers identified intrinsic motivation, wide interests, and openness to experiences as traits that are highly associated with creative individuals (Barron, & Harrington, 1981; Helson, 1999).

Flow is a state of mind where individuals performing a task are fully immersed in their performance. It is the result of a good balance between challenge and abilities to perform a certain task. If an individual is equipped with good skills and abilities for a certain task, and the task is not too easy or too hard for their skills then they are most likely to experience this state of flow. Csikszentmihalyi identified nine characteristics that are responsible for Flow: *challenge skill balance, merging of action awareness, clarity of goals, unambiguous feedback, high concentration, sense of control, loss of self, loss of time awareness, and intrinsic motivation* (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990). In a previous study, Cseh, Phillip and Pearson (2014) investigated the correlation between flow, positive affect, and creativity. Participants of the study reported their flow after completing two creativity tests (self-evaluation and visual creativity test). The study found that flow is highly associated with positive affect, which is also highly associated with creativity (Amabile, Barsade, Mueller, & Staw, 2005). The study also reported a significant correlation between flow and self-evaluated creativity. When individuals are in a flow state of mind, they feel more creative. Amabile developed a theory that explains the association between positive affect and increased creativity in organizations. Her theory of affect and creativity in organizations states that positive affect is highly associated with creativity (Amabile, et al., 2005). In another study positive affect was reported to be connected with “associative thought-behavior pattern”, which tends to increase divergent thinking and creativity (Cseh, et al., 2014). In his book *Play*, Brown (2010) described the state of play as experiencing flow. When playing, individuals lose the sense of time, they are fully immersed, they worry less about going right or wrong, and they experience a loss of self awareness (Brown, 2010).

These studies are a strong evidence of the correlation between play and creativity traits. This study is focused on the creative performance of individuals who perceive a task as either play or work.

Creativity tests

Creativity tests measure cognitive or noncognitive skills in individuals. Some of the important cognitive skills measured for creativity are divergent thinking, making associations, linking and combining categories (Cromptley, 2000). Some of the most important tests in creativity studies are the Remote Association Test (RAT), the Torrance Test for Creative Thinking (TTCT), and Alternative Uses Test (AUT).

The Remote Association Test (RAT) is a test developed based on associative theory. This theory claims that forming new combinations in a useful way is considered creative thinking (Mednick, 1962). Based on

this, the participant is asked to form new combinations by finding links between given words. They are given a set of three words that are from mutually remote associative clutters and are asked to find a fourth word. A given example is: blue cake cottage. The answer to this word set is “cheese” as it associates with all three words: “blue cheese,” “cheesecake,” and “cottage cheese.”

The Torrance Test of Creative Thinking (TTCT) is a creativity test developed by Paul Torrance in 1971. The test measures creativity through a series of different tests that include oral, written, and drawn activities. The test is evaluated and scored based on three criteria: fluency, flexibility, elaboration, and originality. Fluency is the ability to come up with a number of ideas. Flexibility is the ability to come up with many ideas from different categories. Elaboration is the amount of details added. Originality is the authenticity of ideas presented (Sternberg & Lubart, 1999).

The Alternative Uses Test (AUT) was created by J.P. Guilford in 1967 as part of his Structure of Intellect (SOI) as a simple way of evaluating divergent thinking ability. In this test, participants are asked to list non-obvious uses for a common object (such as a brick or a newspaper) in a fixed amount of time. The responses are evaluated on 4 components: originality/novelty (statistically uncommon when compared to responses to the overall data set), fluency (quantity), flexibility (different categories), and elaboration (amount of detail).

Originality and fluency (creativity and quantity)

Recent studies show a strong correlation between originality scores and fluency scores. In 1977, Nobel laureate Linus Pauling said, “...you aren’t going to have good ideas unless you have lots of ideas.” This idea has been further supported by research that found a positive correlation between total number of ideas and total number of good ideas (Diehl & Stroebe, 1987; Paulus et al., 2011). A 2013 study found that AUT participants who produce more responses had more original responses and a participant’s later responses were significantly more original than early responses (Kudrowitz & Dippo, 2013). The same study found that participants generate statistically less common responses after their ninth response giving those who produce ten or more responses higher creativity scores.

Creativity and patents

Creativity and innovation are two concepts that are often intertwined. Innovation is an applied form of creativity and is sometimes defined as “the combination of knowledge or technologies in original and non-obvious valued new products, processes or services” (Luecke & Katz, 2003). Creativity is evident in early stages (ideation) and later stages (implementation) of innovation (Anderson, Poto nik, & Zhou, 2014). While “patents are not an indication of creativity in and of themselves” (Judge, 2007), they are a result of creativity as creativity often yields innovation. In a study on innovation’s dependence on human capital, it was concluded that a company that

lacks creativity cannot produce new ideas to be transformed into new products and services (Jurickova, 2014). Patents are often not a good measure of creativity because of the economic limitations. While many companies will support its employees who wish to file a patent, there are many creative people who do have the resources to do so.

Assessing playfulness

Playfulness is defined as a variable that can transform an environment or situation to allow 'enjoyment and entertainment' (Proyer, 2012). It is also defined as a positive mood state (Bateson, 2015). Proyer (2011) examined the relationship between 'subjectively assessed' adult playfulness and 'psychometric and self-estimated' intelligence. With a sample of 254 psychology students between the ages 20-63, the researcher gave the students a questionnaire that contained the following measures: Adult Playfulness Scale (APS), the Intelligence Structure Test (I-S-T-2000-R), and Measure for Self-Estimated Intelligence (MSEI). Using the students' exam scores, Proyer evaluated the correlation between their playfulness and academic achievements. Proyer (2011) reported no significant correlation between psychometric intelligence and playfulness; however, he noted a general pattern of playful students evaluating themselves as less intelligent. He suggested that this result could be due to our perception of adult playfulness as being non-serious, or non-conscientious. The most significant finding of this study was a strong correlation between higher playfulness and better grades in the exam. Students who reported themselves as playful did very well in the questions that required readings from additional material. "Perhaps they liked the challenge behind the task and have enjoyed the preparation—or playfulness goes along with higher aspiration levels and the students wanted to have good grades" (Proyer, 2011).

Mark Twain is quoted to remark that "work and play are words used to describe the same thing under differing conditions." This summarizes a theory that play and work are opposites and on a scale where any given activity can be viewed by the actor as falling somewhere on that scale. This also suggests that the same activity can be viewed as play to one individual and viewed as work to another. The word "work" in this case implies a *chore* rather than the alternative definitions of work meaning occupation or effort.

Bergen presents a five-point scale of playfulness with work and play as opposites on a gradient of: free play, guided play, directed play, work disguised as play, and work (1998). According to Bergin's model, free play often has internal control and motivation and is usually associated with discovery learning. Whereas work is often associated with reaching externally defined goals and is highly associated with repetitive processes and without any intrinsic motivation (Bergen, 1998). Greta Fein conducted a study with children where she asked them to distinguish the difference between work and play activities. She determined that work was defined as having an obligatory nature. While younger children referred to play as fun, older children mentioned that fun could

be found in "work" activities as well (Fein & Wiltz, 2015). In this study, we looked at the creative performance of individuals who view the same activity as either play or work. To evaluate their creative performance, we used the Alternative Uses Test (AUT).

Method

This Alternative Uses Test requires participants to "list as many alternative uses for a paper clip as they can think of in three minutes". 106 employees of a large medical devices company, ages 26-63, wrote their responses on plain note cards. When the 3 minutes had finished, they were asked to indicate how playful they found the task to be using a scale of 1 to 5. Participants who viewed the test as work would rate the activity as a 1, while those who viewed the test as free play would rate it as 5. Participants were also asked to write how many patents they were awarded. The Alternative Uses Tests were scored, according to Guilford guidelines, by the investigators on originality/novelty (statistically uncommon when compared to responses to the overall data set), fluency (quantity), flexibility (different categories), and elaboration (amount of detail). This study focused on fluency scores as an indicator of creativity; fluency was scored by counting the number of ideas written on each note card. Previous studies have shown a strong positive correlation between fluency scores and flexibility and novelty scores (Kudrowitz & Dippo, 2013). Fluency scores, work/play scores, and number of patents were digitized and averaged.

Results

The data obtained from the Alternative Uses Tests suggests that there is a significant relationship ($r^2=.94$) between quantity of ideas produced and the ratings of playfulness of the test. Figure 1 shows that when people view the test as play (4 or 5), they average 12 alternative uses for a paperclip. Alternatively, those who view the test as work (1) average 6 ideas: half the number as those who view the test as play.

Figure 2 shows a moderate correlation ($r^2=.63$) between quantity of patents awarded and degree of playfulness perception of the test. Participants who viewed the AUT as play tend to have more patents. Those who scored the test as work had an average of 3 patents while those who scored the test as free play averaged 15 patents.

In this specific study, the participants averaged 11 patents per person. Figure 3 shows that while a high number of patents (more than 11) may result in a higher AUT fluency scores (more than 9 responses), a low number of patents does not necessarily result in a lower AUT fluency scores. While patents may be a result of creativity, they are not an indicator or measure of creativity.

Discussion

Work/Play Score vs. Average Quantity of Ideas

The data from this study supports the hypothesis that people who view the Alternative Uses Test (AUT) as free play, rather than work, will have higher creativity scores on the AUT test. Previous studies have shown

Figure 1. Work/Play Score vs. Average Quantity of Ideas.

Figure 2. Work/Play Score vs. Average Quantity of Patents.

Figure 3. Quantity of Ideas vs. Quantity of Patents.

that more original uses for a paperclip are developed after the ninth idea (Kudrowitz & Dippo, 2013). In this study, the participants who viewed the test as free play averaged 12 ideas while those who viewed the test as work only developed an average of six ideas. According to prior studies, these individuals are less likely to uncover the more novel and thus creative ideas.

From this study, it is difficult to determine if viewing the test as play results in higher creativity scores or if creative individuals tend to simply view this type of test as play. These alternatives sound similar, however, there is a difference between being more creative because of play and creative people viewing creative tasks as play. It is likely that individuals who enjoy divergent thinking activities are better at divergent thinking. When one is challenged appropriately they are more likely to be in a state of flow and more likely to view the activity as play (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990). It is also likely that individuals who viewed the AUT as play were in a positive mood, which leads to a better performance in dimensions associated with creativity and increase cognitive variation (Amabile, et al., 2005). It is also possible individuals who viewed the AUT as work found it either too easy or too challenging. This would likely result in lower engagement, fewer ideas, and less play. It will also result in negative affect such as frustration, which would decrease their creative performance (Amabile, et al., 2005). However, if either or all of these factors are playing a role in the outcome, the results still indicate that individuals who view the AUT as play are also more prolific idea generators.

To relate this to the real world, individuals should try to find the playful elements in their activities if they want to be more prolific and creative in those activities. Alternatively one could choose careers that they already view as play. As Mary Poppins says “find the fun and snap, the job’s a game.” Industry and academia could actively promote playfulness in work environments if they want to encourage more creative output. However, further research is needed on the effect of playful environments on creative output. It is possible that an activity is no longer play when the activity is externally motivated.

Quantity of Ideas vs Quantity of Patents

Although patents were not the intended measure of creativity in this study, this data was available and worth exploring. Some research does use patents as a metric for rating the innovativeness/inventiveness of an individual (Boh, Evaristo, & Ouderkerk, 2013). This study found that participants with more patents rated the AUT as more playful. As this study has shown that viewing the AUT test as play yields more original ideas, it is logical that participants with more patents would also think of more original ideas. The converse, however, was not true. Those with fewer patents did not necessarily think of fewer original ideas. While patents may be the result of a highly creative group or individual, one cannot conclude that the number of awarded patents is a strong indicator of creative potential. Many people do not have the support to obtain a patent, filing a patent takes time and money,

and creative work is not always patentable. However, in a large medical device company where engineers and scientists are expected to produce patentable material and the resources are freely available for them to receive the patents, it is likely that patents would become more relevant in assessing creativity of an individual.

Conclusion

To explore the relationship between play and creativity, the Alternative Uses Test, was given to a group of scientists and engineers. This study supports the hypothesis that people who view this creativity test as play will also be more creative with the test. Fluency or quantity was used as the metric to assess creativity and playfulness was subjectively rated by participants using a 5-point scale of work to play. The data shows that the participants who viewed the AUT as play produced twice as many ideas as the participants who viewed the AUT as work. As the participants are employees of a large medical device company, there was sufficient data available to compare these results to the number of patents each individual was awarded. The data shows that those who view the test as play also tend to have more patents. Low AUT scores did not, however, directly translate to a lower number of patents. While it is difficult to determine if creative individuals view the Alternative Uses Test as play because they are good at it or if these individuals are good at the test because they approach it as play, it can be concluded that a playful mindset has a strong relationship to more creative and perhaps more innovative results.

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The new wheelchair symbol: enabling or disabling disability? A structuralist analysis on the plausibility of the new ISA.

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Abstract In 2012, a new International Symbol of Access (ISA) has been introduced by designers Sara Hendren and Brian Glenny as a counter-image to the ubiquitous wheelchair symbol of Karl Montan. By presenting a new symbol, the designers wanted to draw attention to some of the visual attributes of the former symbol they found problematic, such as its passive and robot-like depiction of a human being, while simultaneously addressing, in a broader sense, the place and the degree of acceptance of the disabled within society. Comparing the two sides of this 'design activism', that is creating a more clear and intelligible sign connoting disability and raising a social discussion concerning the disabled, will be the focus of the essay, assessing how the emotional-driven reasons for creating the new symbol might transcend its functionality as plausible 'ISO symbol'.

Keywords Disability, Sign and symbols, The International Symbol of Access (ISA), Connotation, Emotional design

Introduction

Logo's and signs. They are all around us and have become so integrated in every day's transactions all over the globe – pointing the way, indicating information, or showing access – that they appear to have become ubiquitous. Overall catheterized by being simple and straightforward, they are instantly recognized and consequently, according to N. Klein, 'Logos [and signs] have become the closest thing we have to an international language, recognized and understood in many more places than English' (as cited in Berman, 2013, p. 54). The International Symbol of Access (ISA), the wheelchair symbol designed by Karl Montan in 1969, is said to be one of the five most recognized signs in the world today (RI Global, n.d.) (Figure 1).

In the beginning of September 2014, an article was published in the Dutch newspaper *De Volkskrant* announcing that recently a new wheelchair symbol had been developed (Figure 2), aiming at replacing the previous International Symbol of Access (Schoorl, 2014). This act draws attention to the symbols as such. Comparing the two signs, the changes that have been made are quite noticeable. Even though the blue background has stayed intact, the white lines have clearly altered in some ways. The arm moving backward, the body bended forward, the upward leg and the diagonal cutting through the wheel: the new symbol depicts the disabled in a more active way. Interestingly, it is especially when the new sign is introduced that suddenly the stiff, passive and robot-like depiction of a human being in the former symbol comes to the fore: ubiquitousness (i.e. invisibility) moves to awareness (i.e. visibility).

Figure 1. Karl Montan, *The International Symbol of Access*, 1969

Figure 2. Sara Hendren and Brian Glenny, *The Accessible Icon Project*, 2012

This was in fact the intention of the new ISA. By creating a more 'active' sign, designers Sara Hendren and Brian Glenny wanted to draw attention to some of the visual attributes of the previous symbol they found problematic. Their aim was generating discussion on the ubiquitous International Symbol of Access and, in a broader sense, at addressing the problems surrounding the disabled, being a rather neglected, undervalued and misprized group of society (VanHemert, 2013). As honest and sincere as this project may be, a certain ambiguity can be highlighted. Paradoxically, the official website of the new ISA states: 'People with disabilities have a long history of being spoken for' (The Accessible Icon Project, n.d.). The question that comes to the fore then is how the new symbol differs from not doing precisely the same. Moreover, looking at the design from a purely visual angle, the representativeness or veracity of the sign shed a doubt insofar as it wields an unnatural,

disproportionate pose. In this way it can be argued that the symbol conveys in fact more about the non-disabled, wanting to provide a counter-image and addressing a problem, rather than truly providing a different, innovative way of portraying disablement. In order to assess this assumption and the nature of the symbol, the following research question has been formulated: *To what extent does the message of the new ISA transcend its functionality as plausible 'ISO symbol' and in what ways does the sign reflect upon the relation between the disabled and non-disabled?*

This question assumes that more can be deduced from an artefact than simply being studied as an object that serves a certain function. In the latter case, that would be the ISA connoting disability and accessibility: indicating where disabled people can park, enter, sit, etc. The former encompasses a premise that has been expressed by material culture studies: 'Scholars working in the field of material culture studies aim to analyse how these relations [what objects do for and to people] are one of the important ways in which culture - and the meanings upon which culture is based - are transmitted, received and produced' (Woodward, 2007, p. 14). Hence, this essay will adopt a *structuralist approach*. Structuralism focuses not so much on who produced the product but rather on what it may or can tell about the society it was produced in: the underlying structures of cultural convictions. Structuralism implies that people obey to certain social rules, without them being taught in a conscious way. The individual is shaped by sociological and psychological structures over which one does not have control (Jones, n.d.). As a result, it is also believed that values, ideas, attitudes and assumptions are embedded within objects: '[Objects] reflect, consciously or unconsciously, directly or indirectly, the beliefs of individuals who made, commissioned, purchased or used the object and by extension the larger society to which these people belonged' (Prown, 1982, pp. 1-2).

In order to be able to determine the 'nature' of the ISA, society and the social relationships at large have to be analysed. The article will start with identifying the problems surrounding the disabled in society, with special attention to the *social model of disability*, placing the designers' motivation of creating the new symbol into context. In addition, 'underlying structures' within Western culture will be pointed out: that is the binary way of thinking. Subsequently, the development of the symbol will be discussed, resulting in a visual analysis deconstructing the sign. This will be done from a rather semiotic approach, as: 'The methodology of material culture is also concerned with semiotics in its conviction that artifacts transmit signals which elucidate mental patterns of structures' (Prown, 1982, p. 6). At last, through these different observations the credibility of the symbol will be examined, resulting in a conclusion speculating its plausibility.

Identifying disability as social problem

According to a factsheet from the United Nations, around 15 per cent of the world's population, estimated 1 billion people, live with some sort of disability. This makes the disabled the world's largest

minority (United Nations Enable, n.d.). It has to be reckoned that the term disability is extremely diverse. Unlike either of the ISA depicts, only about one tenth of the disabled people are physically or mentally disabled and require a wheelchair (Abberley, 2007). Despite these vast numbers, the disabled seem to be far from accepted by or integrated in society. Research has shown that disabled people are more likely to live in poverty, to be unemployed and to face discrimination in the workplace (Smith, 2010). A 2004 United States survey found that in the developed world, only 35 per cent of the disabled working-age people are in fact working, compared to 78 per cent of those without disabilities. However, two-thirds of the unemployed people with disabilities said they would like to work but could not find any job (United Nations Enable, n.d.). Perhaps not without correlation, disabled people are more likely to suffer from depression.

Being disabled has largely been explained from a traditional, medical point of view, as T. Titchkosky (2007) has formulated: 'The processes through which readers and writers constitute the problem of disability as a medical one [...] (S part 1.). The *medical model of disability* holds a rather individualistic approach and says people are disabled by their impairments or differences. In this regard, impairment is defined as long-term limitation of a person's physical, mental or sensory function, an individual deficit ("The Social Model of Disability", 2014). However, Martyn Sibley (2010), disabled himself, remarks on his blog that an individual may have a medical condition or impairment, but that this person is in fact labelled as disabled through three different types of barriers that are constructed by society. These are physical barriers (Sibley: 'When a building has steps, my wheelchair cannot access it and I am therefore disabled'), attitudinal barriers (Sibley: 'When their attitude is around my needs being an additional difficulty, I am disabled') and organizational barriers (Sibley: 'If I apply for a job [...]. If an employer refused to make 'reasonable adjustments' I would be disabled'). What Sibley is trying to argue here is that disability is not so much a medical or individual phenomenon, as it is a social problem.

This idea can also be found within the academic spheres of disability studies. The (British) *social model of disability*, an upcoming tendency since the last few decades, claims that disability is caused by the way a society is organized, rather than by a person's impairment ("The Social Model of Disability", 2014). The social model emerged from the arguments of the Union of Physically Impaired Against Segregation (UPIAS). In 1975 they had stated:

In our view, it is society which disables physically impaired people. Disability is something imposed on top of our impairments, by the way we are unnecessarily isolated and excluded from full participation in society. Disabled people are therefore an oppressed group in society (as cited in Shakespeare, 2013, p. 215).

What this citation illustrates is the distinction

between disability (social exclusion) and impairment (physical limitation). Although the social model does not ignore the 'body' as such, the primary focus is on how societies treat individuals with disabilities and the consequences of that treatment. The attention is focused onto social oppression, segregation, cultural discourse and environmental barriers (Shakespeare, 2013).

One important factor within the social model of disability is the role of the media, defined in terms of mass communication. When the media talks about disabled people, S. E. Smith (2010) notices that this is often accompanied by sentences such as 'in spite of their disability', describing disability as something negative that must be 'overcome' in order to succeed. Titchkosky (2007) has argued the same: through the mass media, people become aware of disability defined in terms of inability, lack and loss. In this regard, disability is something that is 'written into texts' for mass consumption. Even when disability is being evaluated as 'not so bad' or 'not really different', it is already positioned as unwanted, undesirable, or at least unusual; states Titchkosky. Moreover, the existence of for instance disability-related charities reinforce the status of the disabled as objects of pity (Shakespeare 2013). All these different 'narratives' prevalent within society contribute to a restricted representation of the disabled, since they do not include the possibility of claiming disability as a desired status. With this in mind, Titchkosky (2007) refers to the process of meaning making: '[...] we are active participants in making up the meaning of people' (§ part 1). That is, disability is made meaningful by the ways it is said to be: disability as made by culture, a social creation. In this light, the social model of disability has provided a structural analysis of disabled people's social exclusion (F. Hasler, 1993 as cited in Shakespeare, 2013).

The binary western world

Logos, signs and symbols also function on the level of mass communication as they reach many people and transmit specific, structured information. Apart from the fact how being disabled is presented by the ISA, what will be analysed further on, the fact that a wheelchair symbol exists in general already reveals some information regarding the structure of Western society. According to Jacques Derrida, meaning in the West is mostly defined in terms of binary oppositions ("Derrida, Deconstruction", 1994). In this case, the presence of the symbol reinforces the (possible-made) distinction between disabled and non-disabled people. Moreover, Derrida argues that often, within each pair, one of the terms is viewed as being superior or the general case, while the other one is regarded as inferior and the specific case, as the following citation illustrates:

In a traditional philosophical opposition we have not a peaceful coexistence of a vis-à-vis, but rather with a violent hierarchy. One of the two terms governs the other (axiologically, logically, etc.), or has the upper hand. To deconstruct the opposition, first of all, is to overturn the hierarchy at a given moment (Derrida, 1981, p. 41).

Figure 3. The Accessible Icon Project's stickers applied on the ISA in the streets of Boston.

In light of this research, that would be the non-disabled people being superior and influential in regard to people with a disability. The social construction of being disabled then is fed by the presence of the symbol. For instance, it indicates that certain toilets are adopted for disabled people, whereas others are not. However, when the 'physical barriers' prevalent in regular toilets would be diminished, there would be no need for a symbol. In this example, being disabled would not exist.

The development of a new ISA

Eliminating the strong binary oppositions that rule Western society seems hardly possible. However, changing the relation between the two opposites would be more workable. In this light, designers Sara Hendren and Brian Glenny started to create a new wheelchair symbol. They were unsatisfied with the previous ISA, the widely known wheelchair symbol designed by Susanne Koefoed in 1968 and later on modified by Karl Montan, displayed in many public spaces around the globe (VanHemert, 2013). They regarded this symbol as depicting the disabled as passive, dependent people, therefore upholding the negative construction of being disabled prevalent within society.

In order to draw attention to some of these visual attributes they found problematic, such as the robot-like depiction of a human being, they started a street art campaign in 2009 called *The Accessible Icon Project*. A new wheelchair symbol was developed that would display the disabled in a more active way. By plastering their new symbol in front of the former ones, the transformations in signs were observable: an active figure against the old, static one underneath (Baker, 2011; VanHemert, 2013) (Figure 3). In this way, they wanted to generate discussion about the ubiquitous International Symbol of Access of Montan and, in a broader sense, at addressing the (social) problems and stigmatization surrounding the disabled in society (Schoorl, 2014; VanHemert, 2013). Just as the authors discussed above, Hendren and Glenny had identified being disabled as a social construction. The development of a new symbol then can be placed

within, or at least related to, the social/structuralist discourse within disability studies. However, instead of doing so via written, academic accounts, *The Accessible Icon Project* can be seen as an agent that visually tries to demonstrate that disability is mainly a social problem.

This intention to change cultural and emotional values can in a way be related to the *drench hypothesis*, as formulated by Bradley Greenberg in 1988. Whereas the hypothesis was formulated in regard to television programmes, this research will expand it further to encompass all visual expressions and portrayals. The drench hypothesis states that an unusual positive portrayal of a minority group member on television (in addition via other means of visual culture) can have beneficial effects on the viewer's attitudes and behaviour, even though the majority of portrayals of that group are stereotypical (Greenberg cited in Blaine, 2007). To put it into other words: a single visual expression can have a significant impact on viewer beliefs, perceptions, or expectations about a certain group. It would be able to cut through all of the built up negative stereotypes and stigmas in the media landscape and re-educate people, changing their attitudes towards, in this case, disability and disabled people (Sibley, 2010).

Whether this hypothesis proves itself valid or not, it seems to be precisely the new ISA's aim: changing a mentality, as Hendren has expressed in regard to *The Accessible Icon Project*: 'We knew that a mildly illegal act would actually be the angle by which we could raise the conversation that we wanted to raise, which was not really about the symbol's graphic qualities, as such. It was about how do we represent people in public ways and what does this sign, this symbol which is after all historically really profound in what it guarantees as political access, what does that mean to us now' (as cited in Chokshi, 2014).

Initially, this 'guerrilla art' was in fact the final product of *The Accessible Icon Project*. It had not been the intention of Hendren and Glenny to develop a completely new symbol replacing the old one. The art project had been created to identify a problem, producing a discussion, and raising awareness. However, as the public response was highly encouraging and enthusiastic, Hendren noticed that: 'The response that came [...] made us realize that what people were looking for was, in fact, a new icon' (as cited in VanHemert, 2013).

In order to develop a true, adoptable ISA, the symbol had to comply with the *ISO 7001*, a standard of *The International Organization for Standardization (ISO)*¹ that defines a set of pictograms and symbols for the purposes of public information. Apart from its depiction – a symbol that clearly displays a wheelchair and signifies accessibility – the sign has to comply with other specific rules, like the requirement of a 70% contrast between the figure and the background. Moreover, an adoptable ISA demands a completely flat representation. Three years after the start of the project in 2012, a new wheelchair symbol was created, embodying the qualities of activity

Figure 4. The adjustments made for an adoptable ISO symbol.

Hendren and Glenny initially set out to capture but also adhering strictly to the *ISO 7001* standard (VanHemert, 2013) (Figure 4).

A visual analysis of the ISA

Complying with the rules set out by the *ISO 7001* standard, the new ISA is depicted two-dimensionally, without any shadowing or lighting. It is a highly simplified and abstracted image. As for the requirement of contrast, the sign displays a dark, blue square filled with white lines. In contrast with the blue, plain background, the white parts in the centre of the image are evidently the most important aspect of the whole image. It is not striking then that in comparison to the previous ISA these lines have altered in certain ways.

In case of the new ISA, the white lines are divided into three parts: a circle (upper right), a semi-circle (lower left) and a middle part. Despite this division, the shapes clearly form a whole together: they are part of one image and should not be interpreted individually. The former ISA existed just of two parts, and the endings are rather angular compared to soft, round forms that can be found in the new symbol. This creates a more human and user-friendly look. From a semiotic perspective, these characteristics constitute the signifier: the form the sign takes. The concept it represents is the signified. In both cases, the sign represents a person sitting in a wheelchair signifying disability. However, the way disability is displayed – its *connotation*² – is rather different.

In the symbol of Montan, the two groups of white lines represent what is human and what is chair. Hendren and Glenny believed that, consequently, in this design, the wheelchair overshadows its passive passenger (Lazarte, 2013). In the new ISA, the person and the chair are united as one whole, rather than as two separate elements. This would indicate that the chair

- 1 The *International Organization for Standardization (ISO)* is a non-governmental membership organization that give world-class specifications for products, services and systems, to ensure quality, safety and efficiency, and are instrumental in facilitating international trade (The ISO, n.d.).
- 2 Elaborating on F. Saussure's distinction between *signifier* and *signified*, R. Barthes introduced the terms *denotation* and *connotation*, describing the relationship between the signifier and its signified. Whereas denotation is the definitional and literal meaning of a sign (the signified), connotation implies a 'second-order' signifying system. Connotation refers to the socio-cultural or personal associations that might be attached to a sign.

The Icon Graphic Elements

Head Position

1 Head is forward to indicate the forward motion of the person through space. Here the person is the "driver" or decision maker about her mobility.

Arm Angle

2 Arm is pointing backward to suggest the dynamic mobility of a chair user, regardless of whether or not she uses her arms. Depicting the body in motion represents the symbolically active status of navigating the world.

Wheel Cutouts

3 By including white angled knockouts the symbol presents the wheel as being in motion. These knockouts also work for creating stencils used in spray paint application of the icon. Having just one version of the logo keeps things more consistent and allows viewers to more clearly understand intended message.

Limb Rendition

4 The human depiction in this icon is consistent with other body representations found in the ISO 7001 - DOT Pictograms. Using a different portrayal of the human body would clash with these established and widely used icons and could lead to confusion.

Leg Position

5 The leg has been moved forward to allow for more space between it and the wheel which allows for better readability and cleaner application of icon as a stencil.

Figure 5. Explanation of the graphical characteristics of the new ISA by the Accessible Icon Project.

is not a burden to bury, but illustrates it is rather something that is part of many disabled people's life: 'the person is no longer imprisoned by the chair - the chair is merely the vehicle with which he or she gains access' (VanHemert, 2013). It aims at showing that the chair is part of the person rather than the other way around.

Furthermore, in the former symbol, the person is passively sitting in his chair with his arm by his side. This implies that, in order to move forward, someone would have to push him. The new symbol replaces this passiveness by activeness. The elbow pointing backwards, the knee pointing up, the body bending forwards and the diagonal line cutting through the wheel: all these aspects create a feeling of movement and dynamics. *The Accessible Icon Project* has

explained these characteristics in detail, as Figure 5 illustrates, in which one concept has a prominent position: mobility. The symbol is designed to convey the independence of the disabled, their being active people, wheeling themselves rather than passively sitting in their chair, waiting to be pushed.

A realistic symbol?

Despite this unquestionably genuine aspiration, when examining the new ISA from a structuralist/semiotic point of view, different observations come to the fore that challenge the applicability of the symbol. From a purely visual angle, it is a rather complex image to deconstruct. If for instance the head of the person depicted is omitted, then what is left is hardly recognizable as a human body. This is due to the fact that if the symbol would literally be translated to

reality, it would be an unnatural and disproportionate pose. The person would have given an enormous swing at the wheelchair's wheels, moving forward with high speed. In this way, the symbol resembles Paralympic participants. Racing athlete Kurt Fearnley during the 2000 Sydney Paralympics (Figure 6) for instance holds the same posture as the symbol. In order to move forward as fast as possible, his arms are swung backwards and his body and head are bended forwards. The question that comes to the fore then is whether this is best way to represent the less mobile group of society.

Barry Gray, chair of the ISO committee on graphical symbols, has argued that this over-activity might be problematic. His point is that the new ISA design has attractive features, but he does not believe it is altogether appropriate as an indicator of accessibility: '[...] the symbol has to work in static situations. Part of its job is to mark wheelchair spaces in public transportation or indicate refuge in emergency situations [...]. The symbol also marks accessible routes, like ramps and lifts, not designed for speeding. I fear that the proposed symbol could give a misleading impression' (as cited in Lazarte, 2013).

This seemingly contradiction that Gray touches upon – portraying a less mobile group extremely mobile – questions the incentive behind the formation of a new ISA. T. Shakespeare (2013) has argued that a symbol cannot only be studied for reflecting underlying structures of society, but also as a mediator, capable of creating dynamics. As an active agent of human activity (i.e. Hendren, Glenny & society at large), the symbol can be seen as trying to transform societal structures. It has an ideological aspect in that it wants to give a counter-image regarding disablement, redefining the position of two 'binaries'.

By depicting the disabled in an active way, it seems as if the non-disabled (in the embodiment of designers Hendren and Glenny) wanted to show, perhaps too eagerly, that they have acknowledged a problem surrounding the disabled. However, the (over) willingness to provide a counter-image results in the depiction of a disabled person that seems to be moving forward in an excessive way. Consequently, it can be argued that the symbol is the equivalent of sentences such as 'but I don't think of you as disabled'. P. Abberley has argued that such expressions deny a key aspect of a disabled person's identity in what is intended as a compliment (2007). The same can be said for the symbol: it states, almost in a shouting manner, that the disabled are in fact active people, making the sign itself become, rather, exaggerated. By overemphasizing this (over) mobility it ignores the very fact that should be acknowledged: that the disabled are in theory less mobile. In this light it can even be argued then that the new ISA has moved from one end, that is the symbol of Montan depicting the disabled as dull and dependent, to the other end of the scale: almost ridiculing the disabled as being overly active – neither of them hitting the nail right on the head.

Figure 6. Kurt Fearnley during the 2000 Sydney Paralympics.

Ironically then, it appears that the new ISA is not so much intended to 'guide' the disabled, but rather to 'lecture' the non-disabled. The symbol is in fact meant to be viewed by them. The disabled themselves would not need reminding or convincing that they are active, independent people. It is the non-disabled people who need to change their image regarding this minority group. In this way the concept of design activism strongly comes to the fore, reinforced by the fact that the project started out as a street art campaign using design to create a political debate. Instead of solving problems questions were posed (Hendren, 2015). It is particularly in this context that the 'sticking' of a new kind of wheelchair symbol on top of the former one is sound, as was done by *The Accessible Icon Project*. In light of raising awareness, especially this contrast to the previous ISA gives the new symbol its strength as visual agent of the social disability discourse. This could also account for why designers Hendren and Glenny have chosen to stick with a wheelchair symbol rather than trying to find a completely new image for disablement altogether, since, as has been stated before, only one tenth of the disabled is actually sitting in a chair. Moreover, the question that arises is when the symbol will be world widely adopted – its march has already started – whether or not the same ubiquitous effect will occur as was, according to Hendren and Glenny, the situation with the former symbol by Montan.

These different aspects seem to assert that the ideological message is indeed the most important part of the symbol in regard to its functionality. It is revealing enough that the Museum of Modern Art in New York has (already) included the new ISA in their permanent collection, 'alongside other culturally-relevant designs from the last few decades' (Heasley, 2014). The fact that the symbol has been labelled 'culturally-relevant', rather than 'cleverly-designed' for instance, confirms all the more the centre of gravity of the whole design.

Conclusion

In theory it can be argued that new ISA functions as proper, working ISO symbol. It obeys to the rules set out by the *ISO 7001* and signifies disability. Nonetheless, looking at the 'emotional' intentions and the context of creating this new symbol, that is the

former 'passive' symbol by Montan in combination with the recognition of disability as a social problem, certain comments have been proposed.

The *social model of disability* is based on the notion that disabled people are an oppressed minority group and disablement a collective experience. Disability is viewed as a problem located within society, and the way to reduce disability is to alter the social and physical environment (Shakespeare, 2013). Even though the following quote is not specifically related to the development of the new ISA, its resemblance with the symbol's aim is striking.

Historical and contemporary (re)presentations of disability and people with disabilities by the dominant, able-bodied culture have dehumanized people with disabilities and rejected their agency as producers of knowledge. As people with disabilities have come to critique and reject these other-made (re) presentations, *new forms of disability culture(s) have emerged that (re)claim bodily and emotional performance and assert people with disabilities as experts on their own lives.* (Society for the Study of Social Problems, n.d. [emphasis added])

Especially the last part of the citation seems to encompass the purpose of the new ISA. The creation of a more active, mobile symbol was aimed at transforming a mentality by presenting the disabled in a more desirable way, as the title of the article published in the Dutch newspaper *De Volkskrant* epitomizes: 'Disabled person is no longer pathetic on logo' (Gehandicapte is op logo niet zielig meer: Schoorl, 2014). However, it is precisely by having this component that the credibility of symbol is challenged. Although the public response towards the symbol that can be found on the Internet, both from disabled as non-disabled people, is highly enthusiastic (the demand for the creation of a true adoptable symbol of *The Accesible Icon Project* came from society after all), by wielding a structuralist approach, more 'information' could be deduced from the object of study, moving beyond purely praising it as connoting activeness, independence and self-control. Different observations have been made asserting that the message of the new ISA does seem to transcend its plausibility as valid ISO symbol.

The (over) willingness of the non-disabled to provide a counter-image to the previous Symbol of Access has resulted in the creation of a new wheelchair symbol (sticking to this dogma all the same) that displays the disabled in an overly active way. The wheelchair-user seems to be moving forward in an excessive way, therefore almost ridiculing rather than acknowledging the quintessence of disablement: being less mobile. In this way, new ISA appears to be first of all intended for the non-disabled as an educational tool, rather than to indicate access to the disabled population. As a result, one wonders if the disabled – regarded as a social construction - have really 'gained' something from the new situation. Revealing in this regard is the observation made by Stella Young (2014), an Australian comedian and disabled herself. In her show she talks about being disabled in Western society, explaining

that when she was younger she was considered for the 'achievement award'. However, as she pointed out: 'I wasn't doing anything that could be considered an achievement if you took disability out of the equation.' Consequently, she concluded that people with a disability are seen as 'objects of inspiration'. Ironically, their purpose is to inspire you, to motivate you, as non-disabled person. As a group, the disabled are objectified for the benefit of another group: the non-disabled people.

This observation seems to uncover the 'hidden structures' in the creation of the new ISA. It can be concluded that the new symbol says more about the intention of the non-disabled, that is sending a new message to society – to both the disabled (presenting 'being disabled' in a more desirable way) and to the non-disabled (changing a mentality: the disabled as objects of inspiration) – rather than having a clear and intelligible sign connoting disability, acknowledging a society full of differences yet equalitarian all the same. One group is still objectified – however in a different way – to benefit the other; that is to set at rest the conscience of the non-disabled.

Images

Figure 1. The Accessible Icon Project. (n.d.) *Home*. Retrieved from <http://www.accessibleicon.org/icon.html>.

Figure 2. The International Symbol of Access (2016, January 31). In *Wikipedia*. Retrieved from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Symbol_of_Access#mediaviewer/File:International_Symbol_of_Access.svg.

Figure 3. Mars, R. (2014, February 19). Does the international wheelchair symbol need a redesign? [Web blog post]. *Slate Design's Blog*. Retrieved from http://www.slate.com/blogs/the_eye/2014/02/19/does_the_international_symbol_of_access_need_a_redesign_roman_mars_99_percent.html.

Figure 4. CIVA. (2014, February 13). *Accessible Icon Project*. Retrieved from <http://civa.org/civablog/accessible-icon-project/>.

Figure 5. The Accessible Icon Project. (n.d.). *Icon*. Retrieved from <http://www.accessibleicon.org/icon.html>.

Figure 6. Athletics wheelchair racing Kurt Fearnley. (2016, January 28). In *Wikipedia*. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kurt_Fearnley.

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Roles in User Experience Design - Transferring insights from experience oriented disciplines

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Abstract User Experience Design (UXD) incorporates the increasing importance of emotional aspects in user product interaction and aims at creating holistic experiences. In UXD teams, members with various competences and tasks have to collaborate towards a common experience goal. Roles define which tasks and competences are required. Linking requirements from traditional product development and UXD, we defined an UXD role model in a previous project. Nevertheless, UXD is a rather young discipline within product development. But creating experiences is a traditional focus of other disciplines outside engineering design. We aim at transferring knowledge from those disciplines to support the design of fascinating User Experience. We identified relevant experience disciplines and selected the four most promising ones for our analysis: game development, film production, tourism and marketing. Based on an interview study we analyzed a broad range of roles. We joined the main insights into the existing UXD role model – confirming and enriching existing roles and introducing the new role of an Experience Author. Our approach widens the scope of experience designers and supports product development teams by providing required roles on the way to User Experience.

Keywords *User experience, Design processes, Emotional design, Interdisciplinary teams, Team roles*

Introduction

Besides traditional aspects like functionality and usability, User Experience (UX) widens the scope towards the questions: How is a user experiencing a product? What is the user experiencing with the product? This requires a holistic analysis and design of users' expectation, cognition and assessment of technical products (Roto et al, 2011). The aim of User Experience Design (UXD) are exciting interactions and enjoyable stories with products to create emotional customer loyalty – by triggering emotions of the user (Norman, 2005) and satisfying customer needs (Kim et al., 2011). In UXD, members from various disciplines have to collaborate towards a common UX goal. Therefore, it is relevant to define roles which shape UX teams and which have to be fulfilled by people in product development projects.

Figure 1 presents our research approach, aiming at the goal: enhanced roles for User Experience Design. The left side of the figure explains previous work which we use as starting point: In an interdisciplinary research project with automotive industry we analyzed specific requirements of User Experience Design and characteristics of product development processes. Based on theoretical UX background and conditions in real development projects, we joined both point of views into an UXD process (www.designingexperiences.org, Bengler et al. 2014). The roles included in the process summarize and specify tasks and competences of relevant UXD disciplines on

the way to User Experience. The UX roles focus on insights from areas like engineering design, industrial design, interaction design, etc.

Yet, development teams coming out of these fields are not used to focus on designing experiences. On the other hand, disciplines like tourism, marketing, gaming and film industry traditionally concentrate on creating experiences and fascinating their "users". Therefore, we see a great potential for learning from these areas when designing the User Experience with technical products. We have already analyzed important triggers for the emergence of experiences in these disciplines (e.g. challenge, surprise, atmosphere,...) and transferred the experience factors to UXD (Kremer et al. 2015). In this paper we investigate which roles take part in design processes in the experience oriented disciplines (right side of Figure 1).

By building on existing work concerning relevant roles for UXD and analyzing team compositions and established roles in experience focused disciplines, we work towards our goal: extract new role aspects to be introduced when implementing UXD in industrial practice. Accordingly, it is important to analyze the following questions: Which aspects out of analyzed disciplines emphasize characteristics of existing UXD roles? Which aspects of experience oriented disciplines expand characteristics of existing UXD roles? Which new roles can we introduce to broaden

Figure 1. Research Approach.

the scope of UX teams?

User Experience background

This section presents content of the left side of Figure 1. Concerning our goal, we firstly sum up disciplines involved in UXD. After defining our understanding of a role we present the existing User Experience role model as starting point for our approach.

Disciplines in User Experience Design

User Experience Design – due to its holistic approach – is influenced by a broad range of disciplines (Gube, 2010). Approaches range from psychological to economic and from quality oriented to value oriented points of view (Roto et al., 2010). Hekkert & Schifferstein (2007) categorized disciplines which surround the field of User Experience (see Figure 2). According to the subjective characteristic of experiences, psychology plays a major role. User Experience Design combines the sub disciplines concerning perception, cognition and emotion. Between, further disciplines complement the interplay – either with social and behavioral background (e.g. psychological aesthetics), technical background (mechanical engineering) or customer centered (e.g. human computer interaction). This interdisciplinary field offers a potential for creating versatile User Experiences. But at the same time, different theoretical basics and goals often hinder collaboration. Therefore UXD should not focus on a specific interpretation of experiences, but rather coordinate involved disciplines. Instead of interpreting UXD as a new discipline, we can see it as an overarching link and management function (Saffer, 2008).

Role definition

The highlighted challenges do not only concern theory of UXD. In industrial practice of product development UXD is performed by people coming out of the described disciplines. As mentioned before, coordinating input and duties from various disciplines is the major challenge. Therefore, it is important to define roles which are necessary when designing User Experience. These roles should guide UX team members and enable realization of a common experience goal. As a starting point, we briefly specify

our understanding of a role, before introducing the existing UX roles.

“A role is a bunch of expectations, which evolve out of social processes” (Bergmann & Daub, 2008). We do not focus on social characteristics (e.g. Belbin, 2010) but rather on job-oriented expectations of team roles (Wagner & Patzak, 2015). Accordingly, three aspects define a role: environment, tasks and competences. Figure 3 illustrates these aspects of a role based on the example of a crane operator.

The **environment** describes the subject of work. Wagner & Patzak (2015) name it as “purpose of the role”. Mostly the associated discipline provides this information. In the example of Figure 3, the construction site represents the environment for all construction workers. Consequently, the purpose of the role is contributing to finish the construction, for example building a house.

Figure 2. Disciplines involved in User Experience Design (according to Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2007).

Figure 3. Aspects of a role: environment, tasks and competences.

The **tasks** of a role are the main contributions to the work progress. Wagner & Patzak (2015) combine “tasks, duties and responsibilities” as one aspect of a role characterization, as given task comes with the responsibility of accomplishing it in the correct way. The crane operator’s task is to safely control the crane.

The **competences** contain personal characteristics and skills. Wagner & Patzak (2015) describe these as “behavior expectation” and job-related “competences”. Both are necessary to fulfill the requirements of a role and to process the allocated tasks. E.g. a crane operator has knowledge about technical characteristics and physical behavior of the crane. Accordingly, he is expected to anticipate its movement.

Existing roles in User Experience Design

As described before, working multi-disciplinary is a crucial characteristic of User Experience Design. Roles can help structuring and managing the various fields involved in practice. This section explains the existing roles in UXD which we build our approach on. Human centered design requires the involvement of the following product development roles (ISO, 1999): application domain specialist, business analyst; systems analyst, systems engineer, programmer; marketer, salesperson; user interface designer, visual

designer; human factors and ergonomics expert, HCI specialist; technical author, trainer and support personnel. UXD is located within human centered design. Therefore, it is necessary to build on the mentioned roles but specify them according to UX characteristics. In a previous research project with automobile industry we faced this challenge. Designing a complex product such as a car requires collaboration among multiple participants, representing different departments within the company. Often, each of these individuals has to satisfy different technical and regulatory requirements. Therefore, we defined relevant roles as part of a User Experience Design process: www.designingexperiences.org (Bengler et al., 2014).

Figure 4 introduces the five UXD roles according to designingexperiences.org. Table 1 exemplarily presents the full description of the Experience Designer; followed by brief descriptions for the four other roles.

- *The Human Factors Expert analyzes and evaluates the User Experience with appropriate methods and tools and reveals potentials from the user’s point of view.*
- *The Developer is up to date concerning technologies, develops and integrates concepts*

Figure 4. Roles in the User Experience Design process (www.designingexperiences.org).

and implements the story into the technical product.

- **The Storykeeper** directs the project to maintain the story, monitors requirements, guides as a consultant and represents the project to management.
- **The Customer Expert** has customer insights and knowledge about the global market, quantifies customer motives and communicates the User Experience

A detailed description of all roles is available online. Different sub roles specify each role with tasks and com-petences, as shown in Table 1 on the example of the Experience Designer. The original online description lists tasks and competences but does not clearly separate them. According to our definition of a role, we sep-arated the role description into these two aspects, which is a change to the original appearance. The general environment is the field of product development. Summing up, roles are not representing certain positions in a company, but competences and tasks which are necessary for certain development steps in the Experience Design process. The UXD roles represent the members of an Experience Design team. We use these roles as foundation. In order to define enhanced, holistic roles for experience creation, we revise them by including insights from experience oriented disciplines (see Figure 1).

Research approach: analyzing experience oriented disciplines

We examined disciplines that focus on creating experiences to enhance roles for User Experience Design. When having analyzed most valuable experience factors in other disciplines in a previous study, we worked out criteria to extract the most promising disciplines (Kremer et al., 2015). For our present work we revised these criteria and came up with the following criteria to select relevant disciplines out of the identified experi-ence areas: sports, adventure events, shopping events, gastronomy, concerts, tourism, marketing, gaming and film production.

- **Know-how:** *The discipline should systematically develop experiences for people based on a design process, driven by several roles. This excludes random occurrences of experiences.*
- **Commercial benefit:** *In general, people should be willing to pay for the experiences and the producer should aim at profit by selling the*

experiences.

- **Popularity:** *Most people should already have had an experience in the field.*
- **Availability:** *The discipline should provide access for collecting data through interviews. This involves reach-ing contact persons and their willingness to take time for an interview.*

According to these criteria we rejected several disciplines (e.g. gastronomy due to availability concerns). The four selected disciplines are: **tourism, marketing, gaming and film production**. We chose semi-structured interviews as method to collect data from the professional practice, because we wanted to use the advantage of getting direct in-depth information from experts. The interview guideline consisted of three major parts:

- *What is an experience from your (organizational) point of view? What are the experience factors?*
- *How is the user's experience planned and developed?*
- *Which roles are involved in the experience development? And what are their tasks and competences?*

The organizations for our interviews we found through an online search. The search terms consisted of an alternation of the word “experience” connected with a discipline-related word – e.g. “adventure travel”. We performed in-depth interviews with employees from 14 organizations. These interviews resulted in a list of experience factors for each discipline (roles’ environment) and role descriptions (specified into tasks and competences). We confirmed the information about the roles through the description of the German federal employment agency, where we could find a brief description of each role from one comparable source. For promising roles we performed a further literature research. To extract common findings, we merged similar characterized roles in each discipline. Nevertheless, it was crucial to keep the original role descriptions in focus. In this way, we ensured a balance between summarizing general findings and enabling transfer them to UXD on the one hand as well as keeping valuable original information on the other hand.

In a further step we compared the extracted roles with the existing UXD roles described before. The comparison focused on the role characterization: tasks, competences and environment. The result of this

Table 1. Experience Designer (according to www.designingexperiences.org)

Experience Designer	Tasks	Competences
		Creative Person
	...contributes creative ideas	...can think laterally and cross borders
		Storyteller
	...creates story and storyboard.	...has a creative and psychological understanding, ...can convey ideas, ...is able to tell stories.
		Experience Designer
	...translates story into concepts.	...has a comprehensive approach for implementing the concept.

research is adding value to the existing model – by new roles, adjusting roles and confirming roles.

Results

In this section we describe the results of our approach. Starting with factors which shape experiences in each specific discipline, we present discipline specific roles and the enhanced roles for UXD.

Experience factors: the roles' environment

The experience factors form the environment of the roles in each discipline. Table 2 lists the factors discipline wise – providing the goals for experience designers in the different professional fields. They are a collocation from the interviews and examination of the “products” of each discipline (e.g. touristic offer, advertisement, online game and movie).

While a deep understanding of the user and triggers for experiences is required in all discipline, there are differences concerning the specific characteristics of experiences. For example in tourism experiences are mostly created by exceptional and unknown/new situations. This is comparable to extraordinary User Experience which emerges out of special or memorable events with products according to Schifferstein & Hekkert (2008). An exemplary tourist offer could be a mountain tour to climb Mount Kilimanjaro. To most people this journey would be an experience and could meet several named factors. To someone, who has not been in Tanzania, it is a new country, new culture, and a magnificent nature and the encounter of people plays a big role when climbing the mountain with the local folks. At the same time the ascent is a tough mountaineering expedition and borderline experience. The daily routine of experience designers in tourism is creating newness and designing a program with memorable situations.

In contrast to this, gaming industry does not focus on singular but on continuous experiences – e.g. by

providing long lasting fun, sensual appeal and challenge. In marketing and film production, experience designers have to design a coherent marketing concept or film structure which allows the visitor to project himself into the story

Experience creating roles of each discipline

Table 3 presents an overview of the roles which we extracted from the interviews – separated into four different categories of roles (first column). The first row shows an Author/Story supplier. This role supplies the story at the start of the design process. The roles in the second category characterize a kind of designer. These roles adapt the original story to fit to the product. Category 3 specifies a developer or implementer. These roles implement the adapted story of the final product and have the required background knowledge. The last row 4 shows managing roles. They are located at a higher level of the development team and have to make main decisions concerning the experience creating process.

Table 3 contains only the role names. Each role consists of certain tasks and competences, as introduced before. We present the unique characterizations of the roles as part of the enhanced UXD role model in the next section. Two roles caught our special interest and seem to have a high potential to bring up new aspects for UXD: the **director** and the **author**. The author brings in a totally new starting point and access for designing a User Experience. The director combines artistic and organizing aspects – showing accordance to several roles from designingexperiences.org (see Table 6). Table 4 and 5 present complete role descriptions of director and author – information from the interviews extended with details from a literature research.

Enhanced role model for User Experience Design

Table 6 presents our main result: the enhanced role model for UXD. It is based on the UX roles from designingexperiences.org. The table contains three

Table 2. Experience factors of the four analyzed disciplines.

Tourism	Marketing	Game development	Film production
unknown countries & cultures	emotional attachment	fun and excitement	coherent film structure
encounters with people	memories	appealing design	artistic appeal
borderline experiences – mountain tour / expedition	comprehensive stories	community	emotional attachment
magnificent nature	sense of community	affinity to game content	self-projection of the spectator
fulfillment of dreams		challenge	

Table 3. Experience creating roles in each discipline.

Tourism	Marketing	Game development	Film production
1	Story supplier	Author	Author
2	Mountain guide	Game Designer	Director
	Person on site	Test group	Test group
3	Geography specialist	Technical implementer	Actors
	Product manager		Cutter
4	Tourism expert	Experienced developer	Editor
			Productions manager

main columns: the **name** of the role, the **characteristic** of each sub-role separated into tasks and competences and the analysis **insights from other disciplines**. The new role model consists of six roles. Each role is divided into further sub-roles. Because of limited space we only describe new and adjusted roles and just name confirmed exiting roles in the two left columns. The original role descriptions are available online. The blue phrases highlight the new information, which we transferred to UXD. In the right column, we display the original role description. It is blue if it is new information and black if the content presents confirmed details of existing roles.

The major change to the pre-existing roles is the added Experience Author which we mainly derived from game and film author. This change should lead to **more engaging experience stories for the user**. Further adjustments are the enhancement of the Human Factors Expert and the Experience Designer. The novel aspects of the Human Factors Expert originate in the mountain guide in tourism, which should allow fitting the product with its **story more closely to the user's demand**. Insights from the Person on site in tourism and from the psychologist in marketing enhance the Experience Designer. This change should help to **integrate influencing context factors upon an experience** into the design process. In the following we present details of the three mentioned improvements.

The **Experience Author** is changing the initial development situation. He provides an engaging and inspirational product story at the beginning of the design process. The story is the basis for the further development. This might lead to a stronger User Experience. In the original experience disciplines the author provides a comprehensive story at the beginning of the process. It is an overarching story which provides the framework for detailed subsequent experience story design. Knudsen (2016) describes this process for film production: "The vision of the screenplay will then be shaped by the careful selection of director, cinematographer, editor and so on, and what eventually ends up on the screen may or may not live up to the original vision of the screenwriter." In

Table 4. Characterization of the Director: [1] StoryCrate: Tabletop Storyboarding for Live Film Production (2012); [2] Novel Management Model to Increase Visual Effect Productivity (2013); [3] Moving Cameras and Living Movies (2013); [4] The Film Director Prepares: A Complete Guide to Directing for Film and TV (2010).

Director	
Tasks	Competences
...designs the artistic result,	...requires patience, creativity
...works with the cutter on final edit [1],	and an inner visual skill – like an instinct or intuition,
...makes the principal creative decisions during the filming process [1],	leading abilities, differentiation between being forceful and letting things happen [4].
...designs the camera angels [1],	...is organized and structured [1], [3], [4].
...specifies visual effect details [2] / creates physical, visual appearance [3],	
...decides the set of actors.	

our role model the Storykeeper pays attention to maintaining the initial vision of the author. Concluding, the new role of the Experience Author is not changing the User Experience Design process but rather provides another access possibility to start into the process.

We added an Influence Expert as sub-role of the **Experience Designer**. This new sub-role we derived from the person on site in tourism and from the psychologist in marketing. In both cases they have real insights about what context factors influence the User Experience. So far the Human Factors Expert evaluates the User Experience in the UXD process. Whereas he focuses on the user's point of view, the Influence Expert reveals impacts of environmental influences (e.g. culture, physical environment,...) upon the user and his ex-perience with the product. This stresses the importance of the surrounding/context which shapes the setting of product use. Thus, the Experience Designer unites both analysis and design of the intended UX based on his psychological understanding.

The **Human Factors Expert** has the sub-role Analysis Specialist. We extended this sub-role by the task to monitor the user while using the product to gain implicit information about the usage. This specialty we ex-tracted from the mountain guide in tourism. He accompanies the hikers on the mountain and can gain specific user feedback. In contrast to the Influence Expert he rather focuses on the user than on the context of usage. Another specific aspect of the mountain guide his possibility to influence the User Experience during the actual time of usage. This brings up an advanced way of creating experiences for a user. It allows reaction to the user's desires and refining the User Experience during usage. Accompanying a user in real usage situations will reveal new information about the usage and will go beyond questionnaires or traditional test group observations. In order to introduce this knowledge into the development process, the Human Factors Expert needs to be very sensitive and a good observer when accompanying the user.

Table 5. Characterization of the Author: [5] Screenwriting and emotional rhythm (2014); [6] The Total Filmmaker: Thinking of screenwriting, directing and editing as one role (2016); [7] ScriptEase: A generative/adaptive programming paradigm for game scripting (2007); [8] Player as Author: conjecturing online game creation modalities and infrastructure (2005).

Author	
Tasks	Competences
...has the idea,	...has expertise in creating and detailing storylines and all the intricacies [7],
...writes an inspiring and engaging story,	...has strengths in the creative process [7],
...creates an order of things, sequence of images, words and sounds that produce a flow of feelings [5],	...has narrative mindset [8],
...creates a living story that excites and moves the creator [6].	...has cinematographic mindset and focuses on visual language and aesthetics as a primary form of communication and involvement [8].

Exemplary development situation

In the following, we highlight our enhanced role model for UXD with an exemplary development situation. The description focuses on the tasks of each role.

Nevertheless, the development process is based on strong co-operation between the roles.

The initial situation is the development of a product, with focus on User Experience. The UXD starts with the search for the best underlying experience oriented story. Therefore the **Experience Author creates an en-gaging and inspirational story with and around**

the product and the user. The following development phases build on this initial story. The Customer Expert now defines the user group and the as-is situation of product usage. Customer Expert, Experience Designer and Developer create the framework for the project, compile user profiles and generate first concept ideas. These aspects influence the subsequent elaboration. In a further step, the UXD team integrates different concepts into the overarching story and the Human Factors Expert evaluates the impact of the story with the help of questionnaires or interviews. **Implicit usage infor-mation gathered from real life**

Table 6. Roles for the UXD with new inputs from four experience oriented disciplines.

The role	Tasks of the role in the UXD process	Competences of	Original role in the other discipline
Human Factors Expert	Analysis Specialist		Tourism: Mountain guide: — always accompanies the users during time of usage — knows the environment of product usage — can influence the user's experience at the time of usage
	...accompanies the user to gain implicit usage information.	...is sensitive and a good observer.	Game development and film production: Test group: — tests the product — values the level of experience
Experience Designer	UX-Evaluation Expert		
	Creative Person		Game development: Game designer: — creates the design of the game — supplies the story line
	Storyteller		Film production: Director: — creates a storyboard/prompt book — decides about the scenes — is responsible for the artistic success — works with the cutter on the final edit — defines the visual identity — has an inner visual skill to create a story flow
	Experience Designer		Tourism: Person on site: — lives in the environment of product use — has continuous contact with the user — contributes this knowledge to product develop-ment
Storykeeper	Influence Expert		Marketing: Psychologist: — knows the influences to a user's experience — considers the impact of correlations of product details
	...contributes first-hand knowledge.	...knows the envi-ronment, in which the prod-uct is used, ...knows the influence factors on a User Experience.	
	Project Controller		Tourism: Tourism expert: — has last decision from business side — knows the market
	Requirement Manager		Game development: Game editor: — knows target group and market — checks the game consistence
Storykeeper	Project Manager		Product manager: — plans strategies for the product design
	Consultant		Film production: Producer: — controls the technical and economic success — makes decisions Editor: — makes decisions about the content and the adequate form of the film

(part 1)

The role	Tasks	Competences of	Original role in the other discipline
Developer	the role in the UXD process		
	Technology-Scout		Tourism: Geography specialist: — knows the possibilities based on the landscape — Product manager: — introduces background knowledge about the touristic area
	Concept Engineer		Marketing: Task related developer: — has specialized knowledge — creates the visceral appearance of the product Game development: Game designer: — designs the game content Illustrator: — creates games through models and drawings — creates prototypes
	Requirement Developer		Film production: Cutter: — processes the final touch through a technical expertise (incl. technical and artistic aspects) — has close relationship with the Director (cf. Experience Designer) Director: — decides about the set of actors
Customer Expert	Developer		
	Customer and Market Expert		Game development: Game editor: — knows the target group and the market Tourism: Tourism expert: — is market specialist and knows the discipline Mountain guide: — collects insights from the customer
	Statistician		
Experience Author	Communication Expert		
	Storysupplier		Marketing: Story supplier: — has a precise imagination for the concept — supplies the basis for the following development Game development: Game author or inventor: — introduces the story, which is the initial situation for the development — can be a professional inventor, or anyone with an idea Creative director: — has a vision for the game, including a auditory and visual identity Film production: Author: — creates the base for the production — is a creative idea provider — works together with the Producer

(Table 6 part 2)

observations supports fully aiming on an experience for the user group. Thereafter, Experience Designer, Customer Expert and Developer develop the story further to a storyboard, which gives detailed information about the entire interaction of user and product. At this step the **Experience Designer ensures the intended User Experience with his knowledge about environmental influencing factors.** The Storykeeper looks out for maintaining the vision of the Experience Author's initial story along the total process, to ensure that the inspirational aspects do not get lost while translating them into a physical product subsequently. The Developer designs the product components, while the Human Factors

Experts evaluates the actual User Experience. The Customer Expert communicates the underlying story, highlights UX-potentials and creates a feeling of anticipation. Throughout the development process, the Storykeeper screens the achievement of UX milestones (Kremer et al, 2014).

Discussion

We chose interviews for collecting our information. This is due to the fact that we wanted to gather knowledge directly from experts in experience oriented disciplines. To get reliable results we contacted several experts in each discipline. A further advantage of interviews was the chance of asking

further questions. This gave us the possibility to get answers of the same expert regarding: the experience factors, the involved roles in the experience creation process and the roles' tasks and competences. We confirmed our results through literature – focusing on the author and the director. Our study revealed promising exemplary insights from experience oriented disciplines. The fact that most insights confirmed the existing UXD roles of designingexperiences.org supports direction of the initial role model. Nevertheless, further literature review and analysis of sources and disciplines outside the scope of this study might lead to novel findings – confirming the found roles but uncovering new roles as well.

The main new role which we transferred to UXD is the Experience Author. The high value of this role is the enthusiastic story for the product. But attention has to be paid not to change the actual UXD process. The other team members might not accept the story. For that reason, the team and especially the Experience Designer is processing the given story in further steps.

Furthermore, the mountain guide has a unique possibility to create or influence the User Experience during usage. He can interact with the user during the experience. There are first technical ways of implementing this feature – e.g. voice instructions in the car, on a smart phone or on other devices. In addition, we placed the task to record implicit information about the usage as an adjustment of the Human Factors Expert. He accompanies the user during product use to gain implicit information about the user's behaviour. A technical device could as well implement this task – by tracking and analysing usage data.

Summary and outlook

User Experience Design widens the scope of product development beyond traditional functional and pragmatic aspects and aims at fascinating experiences. Accordingly, people fulfilling various UXD roles have to collaborate together. We consider a role as a collection of certain tasks and competences located in a specific environment. A UXD role model out of a previous project links requirements from traditional product development and UXD and served as basis for our approach. As other disciplines are ahead of product development concerning the design of experiences we aimed at enhancing existing UXD roles with insights from those disciplines. Therefore, we identified relevant experience disciplines and selected those, which were most promising for our study: game development, film production, tourism and marketing. In those selected disciplines we performed an interview study and extracted relevant roles for creating experiences (e.g. person on site in tourism, story supplier in marketing, author in gaming and director in film production). Each analyzed role reveals possible competences and tasks for designing experiences and can inspire UXD teams. Analyzing and comparing all roles throughout the different disciplines, we gathered various relevant UX tasks. We integrated our findings into the existing UX role model. Our analysis generally confirmed the pre-

existing roles. As additional main role we introduced the Experience Author who acts as story supplier and visionary towards a holistic product experience. Furthermore, we enriched existing roles: The Experience Designer should also perform as an Influence Expert – having deep insights of the real world usage environment and continuous contact with the user. The Human Factors Expert should (similar to a mountain guide in tourism) accompany the users during time of usage and should be able to influence the User Experience at the time of usage

Our model is a first step towards transferring the gathered approaches to product development. We paid attention to “translating” discipline specific insights to product design but on the other hand providing links to the original experience discipline and not losing exceptional role characteristics. From this starting point, future work will focus on validating and advancing new found UX role aspects – investigating relevant literature which aims at identified potentials and integrating further disciplines in our research. Using design thinking approaches, we want to engage with and learn from people committed to relevant disciplines.

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Promoting connection: Designing social media experiences to support people with eating disorders

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Abstract Eating disorders are characterized by extreme emotions, beliefs, and behaviors related to weight and food. They can cause serious psychological and physical problems and have the highest mortality rate of any mental illness. Research has established the strong connection between disordered eating and emotion, namely that the disordered behaviors around eating serve as a coping response to deal with distressing and overwhelming emotion. Instead of focusing on the behaviors or outcomes of an eating disorder, effective support should include addressing the underlying emotional experience of someone with an eating disorder. Social media companies are at a unique advantage to provide support for those who post eating disorder related content by offering more supportive experiences that better match people's needs. This paper explores ways to address the emotional needs of social media users through designing experiences that (a) make people feel seen and heard by focusing on their suffering and emotions rather than their eating behaviors; (b) help people feel they belong by focusing on activities and opportunities that enable connection with themselves and things they value; and (c) help people feel in control by focusing on resources and information to receive support or take steps toward recovery.

Keywords *Social media, Eating disorders, Mental health, Well-being, Emotion regulation*

Introduction

Prevalence and mortality of eating disorders

According to the National Eating Disorder Association, eating disorders are defined by extreme emotions, beliefs, and behaviors about weight and food (NEDA, 2016). They include anorexia nervosa, which is characterized by severe weight loss and self-starvation; bulimia, characterized by consuming excessive calories followed by self-induced purging to rid oneself of calories consumed; binge eating disorder, which involves repeated episodes of consuming large amounts of food without control; and eating disorder not otherwise specified, which includes partial symptoms of the aforementioned eating disorders (NEDA, 2016). A recent study of a nationally representative sample of adolescents found that 6.1% of the people ages 13 to 18 years old in the United States met diagnostic criteria for an eating disorder (Swanson, et al., 2011), with women diagnosed at ten times the rate as men (American Psychiatry Association, 2013). Prevalence of eating disorders across countries and cultures has steadily increased over the years, often attributed to globalization and urbanization, which brings with it increased media exposure and promotion of the Western thin ideal of beauty (Smink, Hoeken, & Hoek, 2012). Due to the mental toll and physical demands of the disorder, it has the highest mortality rate of any mental illness (Lozano et al., 2012), with lifetime

mortality estimated at approximately 5-20% (Sullivan, 1995).

Eating disorders and emotion

There is no clear consensus on the cause of eating disorders, though decades of research have identified many contributing factors that can be psychological (low self-esteem, depression, lack of control), interpersonal (difficult personal relationships, history of abuse), social (cultural pressure to be thin, specific definitions of beauty), or biological (unbalanced chemicals related to appetite and digestion, genetic; NEDA, 2016). Compared to common misconceptions, weight and food are not often considered causes, rather are thought to be tactics to control or avoid extremely distressing and overwhelming feelings and emotions. People with an eating disorder may be using the control of food "as a way to cope with painful emotions and to feel in control of one's life" (NEDA, 2016). Thus, people with eating disorders use the behaviors commonly associated with the disorder – food restriction, bingeing, purging – to regulate their emotions. Haynos and Fruzzetti (2011) describe this cycle in more detail with people diagnosed with anorexia nervosa. People with anorexia nervosa were often highly sensitive and emotional as children and have a history of experiencing invalidating responses to their emotions. They learn to distrust or be fearful of their emotions, thereby encountering even an ordinary emotional event will cause them great stress

and to become emotionally disregulated. This takes the form of heightened arousal and anxiety, which feels threatening and overwhelming and is subsequently met with overt efforts to try to reduce, remove, or avoid the emotion through starvation, excessive food consumption, or extreme behaviors to eliminate calories consumed. People close to those with an eating disorder often focus on the behaviors or outcomes (“Why don’t you just eat more?” or “You look so skinny!”) rather than noticing or attending to the underlying emotion or psychological pain that is causing these symptoms. This experience further invalidates the feelings of those with an eating disorder and heightens the emotional vulnerability they already experience, leading to a vicious cycle of them becoming overwhelmed by their feelings and implementing maladaptive eating strategies to cope with the deeply felt emotions. Similar emotional processes have been put forth for both bulimia and binge eating disorders as well (Chen, Matthews, Allen, Kuo, & Linehan (2008). As such, eating disorders and emotion are intimately tied – eating disorders may arise as a coping mechanism to deal with overwhelming emotions and also produce more negative emotions as a consequence of the demands of the disorder.

Eating disorders and social media

The media and exposure to unrealistic ideals of beauty is also considered to be a contributing factor to eating disorders (NEDA, 2016), and social media may be an influence as well. Studies indicate that active involvement in social media can be harmful when people use these sites to find and create communities around their disorder. Preliminary research found a correlation between more time spent online and higher levels of disordered eating among females (Mabe, Forney, & Keel, 2014) and receiving negative comments on posts may increase risk for disordered eating (Hummel & Smith, 2014). More carefully controlled studies are needed to fully understand if and how social media sites influence disordered eating, in addition to understanding protective factors that may limit any such effects.

Designing for mental health

Much of the previous work on designing for mental health has focused on environmental design. Urban design suggests access to greenery, open space, mixed land use, and places for community gatherings are key principles to health (Jackson, 2003). Organizations have been formed to create innovative solutions to the physical and structural aspects of mental health units – instead of a focus on security, seclusion, and safety they are using design principles to move toward environments that promote and support healing. This often involves designs that incorporate natural light, color, nature, and art (DiNardo, 2013).

Designs for mental health focused on technology have been a more recent development. Recognizing that more people are receiving health information through technology, Choe, Duarte, and Kientz (2010) suggested that this technology should focus on building trust, being honest, instilling hope, presenting the information simply, and acknowledging the emotional

discomfort the patient is experiencing. New apps designed for supporting mental health such as Ginger.io and Headspace have taken a similar approach by focusing on simplicity—of information provided and of design—and communicating and presenting visuals in a warm, minimalistic way. Most prominent social media companies offer information pages about mental health but few specifically focus on eating disorders, with Facebook, Instagram, and tumblr being exceptions. These sites offer dedicated information pages about eating disorders and how to receive or offer support. But research is needed to understand what kinds of support people experiencing an eating disorder most need from technology (e.g., should the eating disorder or eating behaviors be the focus or instead should the focus be on the underlying emotions?). Additionally, most of this information and support comes in the form of a static webpage with lines of text. Further research is needed to explore different design options for more engaging, visually appealing ways to deliver information (e.g., is it best to communicate through blocks of text or are images or other visuals helpful?).

Designs for social media to better support those with eating disorders

Some have suggested limiting social media use for people who may be at risk for or have a history of eating disorders (e.g., Mabe, Forney, & Keel, 2014), but given that social media is a large part of many people’s lives and there are also many positive benefits to being socially connected online other ways to address this concern warrant exploration. Accordingly, this paper will discuss the opportunity for social media companies to design tailored experiences to better support people who are struggling with eating disorders. One such avenue is targeting and redesigning the information people see when they have posted something related to eating disorders that has been flagged by another user. We will use Facebook’s platform as an example given the pre-existence of support provided when someone flags another’s post as promoting or struggling with an eating disorder – if the post is deemed a credible concern Facebook will provide information, which includes a number to a helpline, to the person who posted the eating disorder-related content.

This paper seeks to address two primary questions: (1) what are the most effective methods of supporting people with an eating disorder? and (2) what aspects or guiding principles should be used to most effectively address emotional aspects of eating disorders through design? No user data or posts were analyzed for this project. Facebook will be used to develop a proof of concept model that can then be expanded to other online and social media sites.

Method

Participants

A cross-functional team of product design ($N = 2$), user experience research ($N = 2$), content strategy ($N = 1$), and product management ($N = 1$) formed a working group to better understand eating disorders and how they play out on social media. The team consulted with

researchers and clinical psychologists who specialize in eating disorders ($N = 3$), representatives from the National Eating Disorder Association ($N = 2$), an eating disorder activist ($N = 1$), and people who have had a past history or are currently struggling with an eating disorder ($N = 12$, *Median Age* = 26). All participants were female (we had hoped to also talk to male participants but due to tight recruitment timelines and lower frequency of diagnoses we were not able to schedule them).

Procedure

The main goals of the study were to (1) understand the most effective ways to support people with an eating disorder and (2) to identify topics that could be turned into design principles to guide creating new support flows for online spaces. In order to address these aims, we hosted discussions and conducted interviews with a diverse group of people knowledgeable about eating disorders.

Our team first met with the researchers, psychologists, activist, and nonprofit all together as a group. We asked the researchers and clinicians about how emotions play into eating disorders and what support people most need and resonate with. We asked the group for ideas of ways social media companies could be more proactive in creating healthy online spaces and providing better support to people who are struggling with disordered eating.

Our team then met individually with people with a past or current eating disorder. Each person was asked to briefly describe their experience with disordered eating and the main challenges they faced. They were also asked how they would best like to be supported. Given the sensitive nature of the topic, these research interviews were moderated by trained clinical psychologists who specialize in eating disorders. At the end of the interview, the psychologist would check in with each participant to assess how she was feeling and would debrief with each person as necessary.

Results

Themes of support and needs from participants

Based on the discussions with experts and people with eating disorders, we identified themes across all discussions and interviews. The first theme that emerged was feeling seen and heard – the disorder is about emotion, not about the eating behaviors. People feel most supported when others ask how they are feeling or what they are going through, instead of commenting on their weight or eating behavior. The second theme was the importance of people feeling like they belong. An eating disorder can be very isolating and attention is often narrowed to focus on behaviors around eating and exercising at the expense of friends and hobbies. Helping people build and strengthen connection to friends, family, and their community can be very helpful. The third theme was that people want to feel in control. For the people we talked with, their eating disorder often arose out of feeling a lack of control in their lives (not being able to influence complex family dynamics or not being able

to control grades or test scores, for example) so they end up strictly controlling their food intake since it is the one thing they feel they could directly influence. People do well when control is offered in other aspects of their lives – knowing there are options and resources available to help cope would allow people to take charge of their environment and possibly seek out help.

Formulating design principles

Next, we took these themes and turned them into design principles based on participant's needs. To help people feel seen and heard we wanted to be sure to validate feelings – the design should focus on the emotional experience and suffering, not the eating disorder itself or weight/eating concerns associated with the disorder. To help people feel like they belong we wanted to expose them to content unrelated to their disorders – the design should focus on activities, people, and opportunities that could allow people to reconnect with themselves and their community and provide something other than their eating disorder to build their life around. To help people feel in control we wanted to offer resources and plant a seed – the design should be useful, offering information and resources that could help people think about things in a new way or provide first steps toward recovery.

Building Prototypes

Taking the knowledge gained from the interviews, our team designed a new experience for how eating disorders could be handled online. Since our interviews focused on people who have experienced an eating disorder (as opposed to the perspective of people viewing content and wanting to provide support) we focused on redesigning the information screens that a company sends to the person who may have an eating disorder. As highlighted through the interviews, the following pages were designed to support people who may be struggling with an eating disorder by focusing on the underlying emotion and suffering and providing a sense of belonging, control, and information about resources or ideas people could use to help themselves.

Intro screen

The introduction screen (Figure 1) is the first page people (who have posted eating disorder-related content that has been reported by a concerned friend) see when going on Facebook. The main components of this page include a description of why the person is seeing this screen followed by different support options. People can choose between having a moment of peace, connecting with someone, contacting a helpline, or can skip this at any point and return back to Facebook.

The “moment of peace” option was included to validate and speak directly to the underlying emotions behind the post. Rather than trying to tell them what is right or wrong, we offer suggestions on how to alleviate emotional pain and reduce anxiety in small, actionable ways.

The “connect with someone” option was included to address the design principle of exposing people to

Figure 1. Introduction screen.

content unrelated to their disorder. Because having an eating disorder can be very isolating, we hoped to encourage the person to reach out to someone, as texting can often be easier than calling or asking for help in person. Here, we help people choose from their friend list and provide a template for crafting a message to ask for support.

The “contact a helpline” option was included to address the design principle of planting a seed, or removing obstacles to make it as easy as possible for people take first steps towards recovery. We wanted to be sure to offer resources so people know who they can reach out to if they don’t want to talk at the moment. We also wanted to be sure to offer a variety of ways to connect with other people, for those who

Figure 2. Moment of peace – animation.

feel more comfortable talking with a helpline rather than with someone in their social circle

The “skip this” option was included to make this experience optional. Given people may be at different stages of the eating disorder experience, it is important that this step be optional as it may be too difficult for someone deeply in the throws of an eating disorder or unnecessary to someone who is comfortably on the road to recovery.

Moment of peace

The “moment of peace” section (Figures 2-4) provides a few suggestions for how to alleviate distress in order to get to the heart of the matter by speaking to the emotion behind the post about disordered eating. In the first screen, we set expectations and give the person an opportunity to pause and watch a peaceful animation of clouds floating by and tea steaming by a windowsill (Figure 2). We hoped to create a calm environment and shift the mood through artwork and animation. On the next screen, we provide suggestions on things they can do on their own to create a moment of peace (Figure 3). We use photographs from real people to depict the suggestions, as we learned from our research sessions that images that felt authentic

Figure 3. Moment of peace - ideas (left).

Figure 4. Moment of peace - more ideas (right).

helped give people an idea of what the activity might actually feel like and encourage them to take that step. We carefully designed the suggestions so that the easiest activities to do were shown first, based on what we learned about the types of activities that are potentially triggering or especially daunting. In this way we hoped to plant a seed, helping people to take a first step that leads to a greater second step. In the final step in this section, we offer people the option to see suggestions to create a moment of joy (Figure 4). Building on the principle of planting a seed, we suggest more ambitious activities for someone to do that might help them feel more connected to the broader world. For a few of the actions, we give you the opportunity to get started right from the app. For example, you can message a friend and invite them to watch a movie. In many of the photographs we drew on the popularity of animals on social media, since images of animals had a universally positive response from our research participants and were able to alter their mood significantly. Overall, the moment of peace section's goal is to help relieve suffering in the moment that drives disordered eating patterns, and to provide examples of positive coping mechanisms that people can use immediately or remember later.

Connect with someone

The "connect with someone" section helps encourage the person with the eating disorder to reach out to someone they know for support (Figure 5). We learned from clinical psychologists and the people we talked to that having an eating disorder can create a sort of tunnel vision, where everything narrows in on the eating disorder until there is no room left for previously cherished relationships and hobbies. People will often avoid social situations where there will be food or they will use all free time available to exercise, for example. This lack of supporting relationships can then exacerbate the anxiety, sense of isolation, and depression that contributes to disordered eating behaviors. It is extremely important for recovery to reestablish relationships and have social support in times of struggle. Because asking for help can be daunting, we designed a guided process that leverages the person's social media network and makes messaging a friend as frictionless as possible. We provide an option to message or call, if their phone number is available, so the person can choose the method they feel most comfortable with. A main obstacle we identified was that people often struggled to figure out what to say when asking for help. To address this, we provide a template for the message so that the person can choose to just hit send, make adjustments, or start from scratch, depending on what they need.

Contact a helpline

The "contact a helpline option" provides a short list of nonprofit organizations the person can contact to get support (Figure 6). For many people, they may not have someone they trust enough to ask for help, or they feel more comfortable talking to someone who does not know them personally for fear of burdening friends or being judged. We designed this section with the principles of planting a seed and addressing the underlying emotion in mind. Even if someone does not

Figure 5. Connect with someone.

contact a helpline in the moment they see this experience, they are reminded that it is an option, and they now have curated recommendations. We also ordered the list so that the easiest option is first – the ability to text rather than talk. We hoped to make these options as approachable as possible so people would feel more encouraged to take a first step. From our research participants, we learned that a simple directory of contact information felt unapproachable and cold. We revised the screen to include each organization's logo so it is easier to get a sense of who they are and make the options as inviting as possible. It is also important to note that this is one of the only screens that mentions eating disorders. Because of our principle of focusing on the underlying emotions rather than on the disorder, we do not assume or label the person's experience. Instead, we frame all of the options around self-care and social support. This way, the options feel more universal, nonjudgmental, and empathetic, increasing the likelihood that this intervention will have an impact.

Discussion

This study sought to identify the ways people with an eating disorder could best be supported and turn these learnings into guiding principles for supportive

Figure 6. Contact a helpline.

designs. The discussions and interviews with experts and people with lived experience highlighted that people wanted to feel seen and heard, that they belong, and that they want to feel in control. These themes were turned into the design principles of validating feelings by focusing on the emotional experience and not the eating disorder itself, making people feel like they belong by highlighting activities that allow people to reconnect to themselves and their community, and providing useful information and resources that people could take action on themselves. Designs were created to put these principles into action. We took notes from previous research by incorporating photos from nature and activities, in line with past research that incorporating elements of nature could be helpful (DiNardo, 2013). Also in line with previous research, we made sure to keep the content clear, concise, and caring yet unassuming in tone to acknowledge the underlying emotional experience of the person (Choe, Duarte, Kientz, 2010). This study seeks to fill the gaps in previous literature by providing information about the experience of eating disorders from experts and people with past or current histories of disordered eating, and turn these themes into ways companies can design supportive experiences that best meet people's needs and

resonate with them, instead of isolating them.

One limitation of the current study is that it does not focus on the experience of the person reporting the content. This person is very important given the process of people receiving support hinges on the person who sees the content and flags it to Facebook or the social media companies. Though important, this perspective was out of the scope of the current investigation. There are many reasons a person would flag concerning content – people could be reporting eating disorder content because they are concerned about the person, or they could be reporting to get that person in trouble, or they could not have an interest either way in that person specifically but are more so serving as community moderators focused on keeping online spaces safe for others. Future research is needed to understand the different motivations of reporters and which designs would best support or detract from these agendas. Another limitation of the study is that only female participants with a past or current history of an eating disorder were recruited. Though females are ten times more likely to have an eating disorder than males, having the male perspective would still be very valuable. Future user research is also needed to evaluate the designs created and ensure they are clear, usable, and supportive. Other avenues of research could investigate how these designs should change based on the social media company in order to best match each company's tone and target user base.

Conclusion

Eating disorders pose serious mental and physical health risks. Without proper support and treatment they can lead to permanent physical damage and even death. One way to support people struggling with an eating disorder is to address the underlying emotional needs that may contribute to or be an outcome of the disorder. Social media companies have the opportunity to interact with and support people in need when they post concerning eating disorder-related content on their sites. Effective support should go beyond providing a helpline number and instead provide richer information and resources that connect with the deeper needs and emotions of the person struggling – to feel connected, seen, and in control of their experience. The proposed Facebook designs aim to address these needs by providing suggestions of ways people can reconnect to themselves and their lives and find information and resources. The designs should not be taken as a replacement for professional help or treatment; rather they can provide steps and information to aid people in seeking help. They can also serve to plant a seed in someone who is contemplating recovery – the idea behind the designs is not cure people, but rather to provide ideas, inspiration, or motivation that may allow people to take the first step toward help seeking and recovery.

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— *Short Papers* —

RelaxedCare: An iterative user involvement project

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Abstract This paper presents experiences of applying an iterative user-centred design approach for the design and technical development process of the AAL (Active and Assisted Living) research project RelaxedCare. This project tackles the issue of connecting older people, assisted persons, with their families and friends, informal caregivers, via technical solutions. To guarantee the involvement of end-users in the development process the User Centered Design (UCD) ISO 9241-210 standard has been applied in an iterative way. From a project management perspective the ISO standard offers information when to involve future users and different expert groups from e.g. technology development, design and user research in the development process. Lessons learned of applying the ISO standard in previous projects indicate that the procedure of involving different expert groups in different phases of a project results in a lack of overall overview of the project for each team member. With regards to this aspect the UCD ISO standard got complemented with a non-ISO standard, the User-Inspired Innovation process (UII), to include aspects from an individual team member's point of view to the process methodology. This paper presents the findings of the attempts undertaken of combining the two process models for an iterative user-centred design project.

Keywords *User-centred design, Product development process, Product development iterations, User involvement, Empathic design*

Introduction

"Is my mum doing okay right now?" This question is permanently present in the mind of most informal caregivers (ICs). The manifold tasks ICs face in their everyday life routines often result in feelings of being overburdened and sometimes even lead to burn-outs. As Sandner (2014) points out the majority of existing AAL solutions focus on supporting persons in need of care. A representative study (Pochobradsky et al., 2005) conducted in Austria in 2005 showed that 80% of the people in need of care receive their care by ICs at home. More than 66% of these caregivers feel overburdened by that task, which results in a loss of quality of the interaction between the two parties. To reduce the necessity of regularly checking the current status of a person at home by driving by or calling, RelaxedCare aims to provide a system to keep ICs updated on the overall wellbeing of their older relatives in an easily comprehensible and unobtrusive way (see Figure 1).

Iterative user involvement

The involvement of end-users, assisted persons (APs) and their corresponding ICs, started right from the beginning of the project and allowed the project team to get close to behaviours, needs and wishes of the potential users. In RelaxedCare the ISO 9241-210 standard (International Organization for Standardization, 2012) was applied for the UCD process methodology. The international standard provides requirements and recommendations for human-centred design principles and activities throughout the life cycle of computer-based interactive systems. The process is characterized by four phases

Figure 1. RelaxedCare – overall project concept.

and three iterations of those phases (see Figure 2).

Lessons learned from previous projects indicate that closing the gap between the technical, design and user research experts is a success parameter for a technology development project. Therefore we aimed at complementing the traditional UCD ISO standard with a non-ISO standard process methodology, the User-Inspired Innovation process (UII) (Dittenberger, 2012).

Figure 2. User-Centred Design - ISO 9241-210 standard.

The UII combines the guideline for involving end-users with a guideline for the involvement of each team member in every phase of the product development process (see Figure 3).

The following Table 1 offers an overview of the two process methodologies applied in the project.

UCD ISO standard process

After receiving the research grant the project started in phase 2 of the UCD process with the first end-user study, designed as an unstandardized qualitative research study (Flick, 2009). This comparative study employed eight methods in total deriving from the field of design research and from the field of qualitative social research (see Figure 4).

In phase 3 for each method the vast material collected was organized and segmented into sentences and categories. Thus the material was analysed regarding phenomena and significant statements for each user

group in order to create meaning units (Creswell, 2009, p. 186) to be able to define positive and negative product criteria for the RelaxedCare system. Based on the findings of the first end-user study phase 4 of the process addressed the elaboration of different design concepts. Three were selected in a common team election process, were prototyped and visualized with appropriate everyday use scenarios.

Phase 5 consisted of three iterative steps: 1. informal usability tests, 2. lab trials and 3. field trials. The goal of step 1, the informal usability tests, was the early detection of usability and accessibility problems of the proposed design solutions (see Figure 5).

The results of the informal usability test contributed to the first iteration of phase 4 – the revision of the overall concept, the design and the technical functionalities for prototype 1. The main focus at this stage was on the technical configuration. Prototype 1 got evaluated in lab trials (see Figure 6) and offered

Table 1. Overview UCD, ISO standard, and UII, Non-ISO standard, process methodology.

Process	UCD - ISO standard	UII - Non-ISO standard
Goal	User-centred design project development	User-centred design project development
Involved Parties	end-users, different expert teams in the different phases of the process	end-users, multi-disciplinary research teams in each phase of the process
Phase 0		Ignite
Phase 1	Identify need for human-centred design	Perceive
Phase 2	Understand and specify the context of use	Collect
Phase 3	Specify the user and organization of requirements	Decode
Phase 4	Produce design solutions	Assemble
Phase 5	Evaluate designs against requirements	Experiment
Phase 6	System satisfies user and organizational requirements	Merge

Figure 3. Non-ISO standard - User-Inspired Innovation process model..

Figure 5. Informal usability test.

information about the comprehensibility of the user interfaces, the system designs and proposed services.

After the results of the lab trials the second end-user study, iteration of phase 2, has been created as a qualitative research study. The method Design Workshop from the field of design research was applied. Three different sessions, namely round-table discussions, model building sessions and voting sessions in terms of preferred colours, materials, surface structures and size for the development of prototype 2 were executed (see Figure 7).

Figure 4. First end-user study.

Figure 6. Lab trials.

Figure 7. Second end-user study.

Phase 3 passed through a second iteration by the analysis of the material collected in the second user study. These results led to a second iteration of phase 4 which was finalised by the functionality and form definition of prototype 2 (see Figure 8).

To date the project development process has reached step 3 of phase 5 of the UCD process by conducting the field trials with participants of the user groups ICs and APs. The results of the field trials will show if the project is ready for its finalization in phase 6 of the process.

UII – Non-ISO standard process

The description of the UII starts with phase 0, which is a phase the UCD process does not include. The phase 'Ignite' of the UII process addresses the permanent expansion of one's own creative potential, the ability to build bridges to other knowledge areas and the skill to identify new potential project areas. It might be considered as a presupposition (*sine qua non*) for every inspired and successful work. The work of phase 1 happened before the research project started. The UII describes this phase with 'Perceive' which means that on an anthropological level this phase builds awareness for changes and transformations in society, ecology and technology. In this phase the need to relieve the burden from ICs was identified and led to the development of a project idea

Figure 8. RelaxedCare prototype 2.

and the search for appropriate experts, companies and organizations that were willing to participate in the project as well as invest a great amount of time for writing a project proposal. The output resulted in the successful submission of a project proposal for the AAL Joint Program.

In the UCD process normally only experts from the field of social research and usability engineering are involved in phase 2 of the project. Under the step 'Collect' of the UII process all team members were involved in the first method of the study through the Assumption Personas method (Adlin, 2011). The goal to apply this method was to initiate an intensive discussion about the target groups of the project among all team members and questioning and revising the existing teams' mental models. After the conduction of all methods during the first research study the created Assumption Personas got compared with the findings of the study conducted with the true end-users. The step 'Decode' of the UII process, which also entails the sorting, grouping and interpreting of the collected data produced additionally three dimensional outputs of the first end-user study: the foldable Personas cards (see Figure 9) and the Cube of Requirements (see Figure 10).

In phase 4 of the UII process, 'Assemble', every team member was invited to participate in the ideation for the design development. Interestingly, almost nobody except the members of the user research and design team decided to participate in this phase. In the UII process phase 5, 'Experiment', different expert team members participated in the discussion about the developed design proposals of the system.

Conclusion

In summary we can conclude that the application of the UCD ISO standard enabled the addressing of user wishes and aspirations in an iterative way in our technical and design development of the project. At project's start we defined our goal to combine the UCD ISO standard with the UII non-ISO standard to involve all experts from different fields in each step of the product development process. During the work on the project we realized that we still hadn't managed to overcome the identified gap between the expert groups of technical development, design and user research

Figure 9. Foldable Personas cards.

Figure 10. Cube of Requirements.

sufficiently.

By applying the UII additionally to the UCD process we reached our goal to visualize and prototype major findings we've accomplished during the cause of the project in order to make the process phases comprehensible in a haptic way. These attempts were effective and well received among the project team members. Concerning the attempts we made to invite and to raise motivation of all team members to actively contribute to the different steps of the process we can't draw a similar successful conclusion. For future projects we will continue our work on this aspect, plan to conduct team workshops in every phase of the project development process and hope this approach might contribute to the execution of a holistic product development process.

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Getting to the root of the problem: Informing design through the exploration of the gardening experience of older women

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Abstract Gardening is a leisure activity that can be beneficial for both health and wellbeing of older women. Although the ageing process can provide more challenges for this group, adaptation of the activities and the tools will allow them to continue the beneficial activities. To explore the gardening experience of an older female (50+) target group and focus on their perception of the various different tasks, this online survey-based research included a range of different gardening tasks and the motivations for doing gardening activities. Participants (N=89) answered 38 questions regarding gardening motivation, experience and comparison of different tasks.

Moving heavy things in the garden is done by few of the older women and this task is more often done by their spouse/partner. It is also perceived as the least enjoyable and the most difficult gardening activity. Improving this task will empower older women to do this supporting task independently so that they do not rely on social networks or paid help. Tool aspects were found to be important for older women's gardening motivation, and improving on the task through product design is therefore expected to have a positive impact on gardening participation and consequently health and wellbeing of older women.

Keywords *Older women, Motivation to garden, Tool design, Healthy ageing*

Introduction

The population of the UK is ageing: it is projected that by 2039 over 24% of the UK population will be over 65 (Office for National Statistics, 2015). The older population is predominantly female (United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2013), 2013). The health and wellbeing of the growing group of older women is one of the challenges facing product designers. According to ACSM (2007), regular physical activity, including aerobic activity and muscle-strengthening activity, is essential for healthy ageing.

Gardening is a popular leisure activity for older adults in the UK and older women in particular (Dunnett & Qasim, 2000; The Horticultural Trades Association, 2011). Park, Shoemaker, & Haub (2008) found that gardening can meet the recommendations for aerobic activity. It can also contribute to hand and body strength and flexibility (Park & Shoemaker, 2009), retaining attention span and memory abilities in persons with Alzheimer's type dementia (D'Andrea, Batavia, & Sasson, 2008), better self-reported scores on physical function, reduced bodily pain and improved hand function (Park, Shoemaker, & Haub, 2009), greater overall self-reported life satisfaction (Sommerfeld,

Waliczek, & Zajicek, 2010) and greater overall physical health (Everard, Lach, Fisher, & Baum, 2000).

Most gardening activities rely on the use of various gardening tools. Other studies have explored a variety of variables associated with the use of a range of tools (Brown Tebben & Thomas, 2004; e.g. Chang, Park, & Freivalds, 1999; Leppänen, Kallionpää, & Vilkki, 1998; Mirka, Jin, & Hoyle, 2009; Päivinen & Heinimaa, 2009; e.g. Tudor, 1996; Zinnecker, 2011). However, an overview of the act of gardening as a leisurely practice for older women and how the individual tasks of gardening contribute to the overall experience has not been made. To develop products that have a positive influence on older women's participation in healthy gardening activities, this overview is needed as it will provide focus on the most relevant areas of this experience.

Considering the above, there is a need to explore the gardening experience from the point of view of the target group in order to prioritise the improvement of relevant tasks and accompanying tools. Three areas of the experience have been identified and will be explored:

1. An overview of the reasons people do gardening in order to investigate their motivation.
2. The perception of importance of tool aspects to establish to what extent the tools and attributes of these tools affect the user.
3. A comparison of the tasks older women pursue and how they feel about the different gardening tasks to identify the tasks with the most potential for improvement.

The results will be compared to older men to enable the identification of relevant differences between the genders. The combination of these results creates a more complete overview of the gardening experience of female leisure gardeners over 50, which will inform the design for more suitable gardening tools for this group.

Methods

Research design

An online survey using Qualtrics online survey platform (2015) was developed to address the research objectives and was active during the summer of 2015. The survey consisted of 38 questions and was developed in an iterative process; pilot sessions were held with three volunteers of the target group and thereafter improvements to the method were implemented. The project was approved by Coventry University's ethics process and all participants provided informed consent.

The survey commences with an introductory sentence 'One of my reasons for gardening is ...' followed by

twenty potential reasons for gardening, including some generic leisure motivations based on Beard & Ragheb (1983), together with specific motivators relating to gardening and an open text field with 'other reason'. The participants rated each statement on a Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) (Aitken, 1969) of 'not a reason' to 'an important reason'.

Participants were questioned using a VAS from 'no influence' to 'major influence' about the relative importance of tool related aspects versus other gardening related aspects on their motivation to undertake a gardening task.

Questions were included on which tasks people participate in, enjoy and find difficult. The latter two were posed on VAS from 'not enjoyable' to 'very enjoyable' and 'not hard' to 'very hard' respectively. For the tasks participants claimed not to do, follow-up questions were asked on their reasons for not doing the task.

Recruitment

The research aimed to approach leisure gardeners. Participants were approached through Royal Horticultural Society's The Garden magazine in July 2015 and a link to the survey was posted on a number of online gardening forums and tweeted by the RHS several times.

Participants

The participants were part of a larger study, which included 68 male and 142 female adults (18+) that currently live in the United Kingdom, do (some)

Table 1. Reasons for gardening for females and males over 50.

Reasons for gardening	Females over 50 (N=88)		Males over 50 (N=53)	
	Median	Range	Median	Range
It makes me happy	100	73	87	100
I feel in touch with nature	94	100	69	100
Influence how the garden looks	89	100	80	100
Relaxing	86	100	62	100
Feeling of accomplishment	85	100	84	100
The quiet and solitude	83.5	100	57	100
Getting some fresh air	83.5	100	59	100
Growing something out of nothing	72	100	65	100
Healthy exercise	71.5	100	58	100
Sense of ownership	52.5	100	37	100
Create nice environment to have friends round	43	100	47	100
Allows me to develop skills	39.5	100	20	100
It needs to be done	34.5	100	28	100
I like that I can control it	20.5	100	42	100
It gives me something to do	13	100	28	100
Sense of being in a garden community	2.5	100	0	99
Other reason	0	100	3	98
Partner/spouse wants me to do it	0	100	0	99
I do it to help someone else out	0	100	0	86
I am paid to do it	0	58	0	100

Medians on VAS of 'not a reason' (0) to 'an important reason' (100).

Median scores for influence of gardening experience related aspects

Figure 1. Median scores for gardening experience related aspects for females over 50 (N=83). Medians on VAS of 'no influence' (0) to 'major influence' (100).

gardening and have an outside space to grow plants. The data of all males (N=53) and females (N=89) of 50+ years old were extracted from this data.

Data analysis

The data was analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences 22. Descriptive statistics were used to examine initial results. Normality tests and plots were applied to the various scale variables and showed lack of normality, thus non-parametric Mann-Whitney, Spearman's correlation and Pearson's chi-squared tests were applied.

Results

Reasons for gardening

Median scores were calculated for twenty statements on people's reasons for gardening separately for females and males over 50 (Table 1). 'Other' reason

entries related mainly to growing fruit and vegetables and providing a place for wildlife.

Importance of tool related aspects

Results show that for this group of females over 50, most tool related aspects are important with high median scores for suitability, ease of use and weight of the tool as well as tool handle comfort and quality of the tool (Figure 1).

Tasks: enjoyment and difficulty

Participants were asked to rate how hard and how enjoyable each of the gardening tasks was on a VAS scale from 'not hard at all' or 'don't enjoy it' to 'very hard' or 'enjoy it very much'. The hardest task was reported to be moving heavy objects, followed by trimming hedges and pruning trees (Table 2). The least enjoyable task was moving heavy objects (Table 3).

Figure 2. Scatterplot of hardness versus enjoyment of tasks for median values.

Figure 2 plots task difficulty against task enjoyment. The graph suggests a negative correlation between enjoyment and perceived difficulty and Spearman's correlation indicated a correlation of $r = -.670$ at $p = .017$.

Effect of gender

Mann-Whitney tests on significant differences in enjoyment of gardening tasks based on gender show only for weeding (median_{males} = 47, median_{females} = 54, $U = 1643$, $z = -2.63$, $p = 0.008$, $r = -0.22$) and pruning plants (median_{males} = 58, median_{females} = 67, $U = 1668$, $z = -2.11$, $p = 0.035$, $r = -0.18$), with women enjoying these tasks more than men. Gender based significant differences in how hard a task is could only be established for pruning trees (median_{males} = 12, median_{females} = 30, $U = 869$, $z = -2.42$, $p = 0.015$, $r = -0.24$), which is considered harder by women than by men.

Task selection

The tasks that were done by less than 75% of the female participants were trimming hedges, mowing

the lawn, moving heavy objects, lawn edging and pruning trees (Figure 3, left side). Follow-up questions (Figure 3, right side) explored the reasons behind why people do not undertake certain tasks and show that 'Someone else does it' was the most frequently selected reason for not doing an activity for those who had the relevant feature in their garden. According to another question ($N = 89$, female) the most frequent delegate was the spouse/partner (45%), followed by a paid gardener (10%).

Effect of gender

Pearson's chi-squared tests revealed it was more likely for males than for females over 50 to do the following tasks: mowing the lawn ($X^2(1) = 11.46$, $p = .001$, odds ratio (OR) = 3.5), , trimming hedges ($X^2(1) = 5.09$, $p = .024$, OR = 2.2), and moving heavy objects ($X^2(1) = 17.32$, $p < .001$, OR = 5.4). In contrast, for pruning plants ($X^2(1) = 3.975$, $p = .046$, OR = 7.1), females were more likely to complete the task.

Table 2. Perception of how hard a task is on a VAS of 0-100 for females over 50. Respondent numbers vary based on the gardening tasks they had previously selected they do.

Difficulty of a task (0-100)			
Task	N	Median	Range
Moving heavy objects in the garden	42	54	100
Trimming hedges	28	35	95
Pruning trees	64	30	100
Loosening the soil	78	18	100
Gathering leaves and cuttings	79	8	100
Lawn edging	59	7	100
Pruning plants	87	6	100
Mowing the lawn	39	6	100
Watering	86	5	100
Weeding	88	3	100
Planting	87	2	100
Sowing seeds	77	0	100

Table 3. Enjoyment of task on a VAS of 0-100 for females over 50. Respondent numbers vary based on the gardening tasks they had previously selected they do.

Enjoyment of a task (0-100)			
Task	N	Median	Range
Planting	87	94	97
Sowing seeds	77	79	93
Pruning plants	87	67	100
Pruning trees	64	55	99
Weeding	88	54	100
Loosening the soil	78	47	100
Watering	86	47	100
Trimming hedges	28	42	77
Mowing the lawn	39	42	100
Lawn edging	59	39	100
Gathering leaves and cuttings	79	36	100
Moving heavy objects in the garden	42	12	88

Figure 3. Percentage of female participants over 50 that do each gardening task (out of total N=88) and reasons why participants do not do a task for the five least done tasks. Participants were allowed to select multiple reasons and the percentages represent the percentages of total reasons given.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to explore the gardening experiences of older women to establish the potential for improvement of this experience so that participation in the healthy gardening activities can be increased. The survey-based study sought to explore reasons people have for gardening, the perceived importance of tools in influencing motivation to do gardening activities and differences between which gardening tasks are done and how these tasks are perceived.

The group of female participants is intrinsically motivated to do gardening with the most important reasons relating to how the garden makes them feel, the result obtained and the connection to nature, with males over 50 giving lower overall scores. These results reflect the passion of older women for this leisure activity. They align with market research that found women have more interest in gardening and enjoy it more than men (The Horticultural Trades Association, 2011). Gardening is a source of happiness that provides older women with both mental and physical wellbeing. As such, they do not need to be pushed to the activities, but it is instead imperative to remove any barriers in their current experience to enable them to continue to do the activities.

Tool aspects were found to be an important influence to participants' motivation to do gardening activities, especially the suitability, ease of use and weight of the tool as well as comfort of the tool handle. If these tool aspects are not optimal in the perception of the older women, these results imply that this might negatively impact their motivation to do the activities. In turn, improving these tool aspects could help to improve the overall gardening experience of older women.

The most common reason for older women not to do tasks was that 'someone else does it' and it was found that this other person is usually their spouse/partner.

However, the reality is that access to this or other outside help can become more limited with age; getting older is associated with increased risk of exclusion from social relationships (Barnes, Blom, Cox, Lessof, & Walker, 2006). To allow women to continue to do gardening, they should therefore be able to work independently.

Nicklet, Anderson, & Yen (2014) suggest that older adults have not been involved in development of gardening activities so far and their input might aid in creating interventions with higher engagement and retention. Moving heavy things in the garden was found to be one of the tasks with lowest participation rates and highest perceived difficulty, whilst also being the least enjoyed. This is a task that has a supporting role to many of the gardening activities. Through co-design with the target group of older women, the task of moving heavy things in the garden will serve as a case study and will be investigated further in future work through which new products will be developed. By focusing on improving this task through tool design it is expected that a positive impact can be made on the gardening experience of older women. This could increase their potential to participate independently in the healthy gardening activities.

Conclusion

The aim of this survey-based study was to explore the gardening experiences of older women. Participating in gardening activities has both health and wellbeing benefits. The older women featured in this study are intrinsically motivated to do gardening. However, the results point for a need to support them with the tasks that have low participation rates and that are considered difficult and not enjoyable. Moving heavy things in the garden was found to be the most difficult, least enjoyable and one of the tasks the least amount of participants did. Tool aspects were found to be an important influence on whether these women are motivated to do gardening activities. When tasks that are difficult and not enjoyable are improved through tool design, it is likely that fewer older women will be dependent upon others to help them with gardening, thus promoting independence and improving the gardening experience of these older women so that participation in the healthy gardening activities can be increased.

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Two design cases exploring development of social emotional learning solutions

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Abstract This paper explores the development of social emotional learning (SEL) solutions created by two design teams. Both teams combined methods from design thinking, empathetic design, rapid prototyping, and evidence-based prevention to answer the complex question: *How might we support social and emotional development in young children (ages 3-6)?* The two teams approached the problem in the same way, but varied the environment of the end-users between homes and childcare centers. The purpose of this paper is to reflect on the two distinct design cases and indicate noteworthy characteristics from them. In particular, we hope to increase and encourage the translation of evidence-based research into real world solutions.

Keywords *Design thinking, Empathy, Prototyping, Social innovation, Social-emotional learning*

Introduction & design project background

Supporting early social emotional learning (SEL), particularly for vulnerable children and their families, is essential for improving the health and quality of life in all communities (Jones et al., 2015). However, conventional methods to translate evidence-based SEL interventions into real world contexts have had limited impact (Rotheram-Borus et al., 2012). The Robert Wood Johnson Foundation (RWJF), recognized the opportunity to develop innovative solutions in this design space, and funded this research design project to solve this need.

Our project began with the following frame: How might we support social and emotional development in young children (ages 3-6)? We were given four months to solve this challenge. This project took place in two locations in the US: Colorado and Pennsylvania. Each location supported their own small design team consisting of 5-8 members. Team members had diverse backgrounds spanning from early education, learning sciences, mechanical engineering, human-computer interaction, and human development and family studies.

It was recognized that the varied routines children experience at home and at childcare centers become a critical part of children's lives and serve as opportunities for skill, knowledge, and behavior development, such as SEL competencies (Greenberg, 2006). Due to the open-ended nature of the problem, the teams decided to explore in these two different end-user contexts: homes and childcare centers. In Colorado, the team approached the problem in the home environment, while the Pennsylvania team focused on childcare centers.

In this paper, we present insights and reflections from the development of these two solutions. This paper will proceed as follows: first, we present background

on the project, followed by the specific designs developed by the two design teams. Finally, we end with a discussion of the noteworthy characteristics from the design cases and the opportunity to translate evidence-based research into scalable, commercially available tools or products.

Colorado design team: solution for home environment

The Colorado team started by observing users in both childcare centers and home environments. After extensive empathic observations, the team discovered that a child's day is comprised of a series of transitions with a significant one being the transition between childcare and home. The childcare centers provide immense structure to the children's day. However, this structure often breaks down once the child is at home. Because of this insight, the team decided to focus on the home environment for the context of the design problem.

This first stage of the design thinking process is empathizing, which entails gaining insights about the experiences, challenges, and behaviors of the children and families. To aid in synthesizing our observations and interviews, the team used the five core competencies of social-emotional learning (Figure 1, www.casel.org, 2015): self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making. When mapping insights to these competencies, we learned that children were often not given the chance to strengthen self-awareness of their emotions. This helped lead us into our re-defined problem statement moving forward: *How might we increase children's self-awareness of their emotions during transition periods throughout the entire day?*

Moving from problem definition to ideation, the team used many techniques to encourage idea formation.

Figure 1. CASEL's Five Core Competencies of Social Emotional Learning (www.casel.org, 2015).

Ultimately, we narrowed down to three top solutions and rapidly prototyped them (Figure 2). These ideas were (1) a handheld feelings and activity wheel, (2) a combination of a feelings poster, writing prompts, and self-reflection, and (3) a feelings embodiment of emotions activity (yoga-influenced). We immediately brought these simple prototypes to our users and gained valuable feedback to move the design forward. We combined these insights, which allowed us to move forward to the next phase of prototyping a fully functioning design.

In the functional prototyping phase, we developed a hand-held "feelings, activities, and transition toy" (Figure 3). The purpose of this toy was (1) to be standalone for children to use on their own, (2) to encourage awareness of emotions through use the mirror and pictures of children's faces, (3) and to support emotionally-hard transitions in a child's day (like bedtime) by identifying these transitions and matching supporting activities with them. We created

three versions of the same design to test user interaction design factors, such as motions (sliding, spinning, pulling), prompting words and pictures, and placement of activities, feelings, and transitions. We left these prototypes with our users for a week so that they could truly embed the design into their lives. After the week, we picked up the prototypes and collected feedback from the users through observations and interviews.

All of the user feedback was taken into consideration as we moved into our final prototype for the project. The most important user feedback included:

1. Creating multiple motions (flip, spin, pull, slide)
2. Specific placement of activities, transitions, and emotions
3. Incorporating audio/light prompting
4. Putting pictures next to all words
5. Ability to switch out words/pictures easily
6. Small, portable size
7. Focus on mirror and emotions
8. Bright fun colors with neutral base

Our final design (Figure 4) was a hand-held toy that helps children recognize their emotions as well as support the many emotionally-difficult transitions throughout their day. A key aspect to this design is that it can be child-led, eliminating additional burden on the parent. The main features are the mirror and pictures of children's faces related to specific emotions. This allows children to see the facial expressions and then look at themselves to see if this reflects their emotions. There is capability for audio and lighting prompts built into this design to help prompt the children to express and reflect on their emotions. The design is meant to be customizable in terms of transitions and supporting activities as shown by the hinged opening. This allows parents to exchange the spin-wheel of transitions in their day (i.e. dinner, bedtime, travel) and the sliding reel of activities to help support these transitions (i.e. sing a song, read a book, go for a walk).

Figure 2. Colorado Team Initial Simple Prototypes: Feeling + Activity Wheel (left), Feelings Posters, Writing Prompts, and Self Reflection (middle), Feelings Embodiment Activity (right).

Figure 3. Colorado Team Second Prototypes: three versions of feelings, activities, and transitions handheld toys (left) and testing with different user environments (right).

Pennsylvania design team: solution for childcare environment

The Pennsylvania team focused exclusively on childcare centers. This team followed the same design thinking process as Colorado: empathize with users, redefine the problem, ideate wild ideas, prototype realistic solutions, test solutions with users, and iterate where necessary. This project flow is mimicked in the following paragraphs as we provide a brief overview of the findings this team discovered at each stage.

At the start of the project, as the design team entered the empathy stage, experts in SEL and empathic observations provided team members with a brief background and tutorials. Findings from initial site visits led to insights that redirected the interview protocol and questions used in a second round of site visits. The second round of site visits provided the design team with deeper user stories and led to the problem statement: *How might we transform early learning centers into places where people, processes, and products are aligned to create, capture, and*

share “a-ha” moments, so that every child has a great day?

This new problem frame helped us move towards rapidly generating ideas. We identified that the large amount of biodiversity present in our samples would make single, stand-alone products difficult to transition across all markets. As a result, the PA team identified the need for a product platform that could be translated across the multitude of childcare center. A platform is a collection of common elements implemented across a range of products; platforms work best in contexts where there is a wide variety user groups, yet there exists common needs across user groups.

Our team identified three common elements across centers and user groups:

1. Teachers feel most fulfilled during a-ha moments with students, yet can occasionally miss a-ha moments or opportunities for these moments due to classroom and resource constraints

Figure 4. Colorado Team Final Prototype. Showing the feedback incorporated in the 3D rendering (left) and the handheld physical size (right).

Figure 5. Log-In Screen and Impact Dashboard of Proposed Digital Platform.

2. Teachers and parents across centers want to communicate effectively with one another, but time and schedule constraints make these periods difficult and stressful
3. All childcare centers have some formal check in and check out process

These common characteristics led our team to develop a platform focused on the check in and check out process because it occurred at every center and provided an opportunity to engage parents. The base platform was an RFID check in process that used check-in and check-out times as opportunities to incorporate SEL activities from evidence-based programs. Add-ons such as at home activities, classroom activities, point systems, and ways to incorporate other environments into an SEL program were explored in the second round of ideation. Our team prototyped a digital interface of the proposed platform system to show teachers and parents how the new check in process might work, and how data regarding SEL development could be collected and displayed in a teacher and parent dashboard. The creation of new SEL opportunities during what is typically a stressful time (checking in and out of centers), along with the dashboard of SEL development, and digital interface for an evidence based SEL program addressed the evolved “how might we question.” Figure 5 highlights the digital interface and dashboard components of our platform.

This solution, which integrates lessons from the fields of industrial design, electrical engineering, and human health and development would not have been created without the transdisciplinary team, design thinking tools, empathic design methods, and rapid prototyping. These factors combined with the fast paced nature of the project and the constant feedback from end users helped shape and guide the development of a truly unique solution that addressed the initial “how might we” statement.

Discussion and implications

This short paper reflected on two design teams as they solved the problem of increasing social emotional development in young children. We saw how the same complex problem can be addressed multiple ways by changing the context of the end-users, in this case between homes and childcare centers.

The biggest takeaway from these design projects was the ability to translate evidence-based social emotional learning interventions into real world solutions. Often, work in areas like SEL is researched and documented in academia, but not always translated into practice (Rotheram-Borusinter et al., 2012). We bridged this gap in our work, and hope to encourage others to do so as well.

We have synthesized five noteworthy reflections on how we were able translate research to practice in an attempt to encourage more researchers and designers to come together to decrease the time from discovery (intervention research) to impact (broad dissemination and use).

1. Form transdisciplinary teams that *combine* expertise from multiple domains to form new innovative solutions (Lawrence and Després, 2004). It is especially important to include both researchers and designers on the team.
2. Become familiar with both the state of the research in the field of study (like SEL and early childhood education in our case) as well as the best practices and tools to support the design teams.
3. Use a design thinking approach that emphasizes immersion into the design space environments as well as rapidly building and testing solutions with users (Grysiakab et al., 2011).
4. Define multiple user contexts as a means to think about the problem and solution in different, yet complementing ways.
5. Set an initial short timeline (like 4-6 months) to develop solutions as a way to get the team bias towards action compared to contemplative thinking.

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Design for people living with mental disorders: Anxiety My "Covachita", well-being for everybody

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Abstract While it can be argued that modern life has allowed us to extend the length of the average man's life, as well as providing important benefits such as the cure of deadly diseases, we cannot forget that the vortex produced by the way of life we have achieved has diminished in several fundamental aspects of our reality.

This study seeks to generate new parameters to respond to the effects of crescent mental health problem in our society.

That is why this project seeks to flow with the times and support new generations living under the shadow of mental diseases by designing products and services that include them in society.

Keywords *Wellbeing, Behavior, Healthcare, Inclusive, Sensorial*

Introduction

This project is the result of a personal experience taken to a research in the design field. I'm an Industrial Design professor diagnosed with Generalized Anxiety Disorder and Panic Disorder thirteen years ago. This is a short paper about the process I've followed for these past two years with the environmental and human behavior to look forward a change in other people lives through design.

With that in my mind I put myself as a case study in order to find insights that lead me and my coworker to develop design concepts which could help people suffering (GAD) to get responses from a person who knows what mental illness segregation is. This project ends with some feedback from a small group of people with anxiety; we keep working with more information, research and validation of the concepts so once we achieve enough information we can have prototypes, this is a first approach to the project Design for people living with mental disorders: Anxiety. "My Covachita, well-being for everybody" which is still in progress.

Mental illness: Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD).

The human race entered the twentieth century in ignorance of what the technology developed by the Industrial Revolution represented and represents to the world and lifestyle. Scientifics began to make deeper studies on depression, anxiety and sleep disorders among others.

While now mental illness occupies a significant place in the field of medicine, in the twenty-first century it was considered a taboo. This last part builds up an ironic case in large cities because it is where many of these diseases have originated.

Anxiety is a normal response from our body to a dangerous situation. We were born like that: in

another time, when we were primitive men we used to need the anxiety alarm every time we had to survive. Nowadays anxiety is a normal part of our lives; everybody has experimented this sensation in their lives, when someone is too stressed at work, at school, in the traffic, with personal or professional problems among others. But for a person whose anxiety is becoming a "normal" part in their lives, the problem involves more than just stress; it eventually becomes a disorder and the person starts to feel anxiety in almost every part of their life and begins to loose self-control as well.

A review that pooled surveys in different countries up to 2004 found overall average prevalence estimates for any anxiety disorder of 10.6% (in the 12 months prior to assessment) and 16.6% (in lifetime prior to assessment), but that rates for individual disorders varied widely. Women had generally higher prevalence rates than men, but the magnitude of the difference varied. (Somers, Goldner, Waraich, 2006).

The problem with mental health is that it is so important that since the second half of the twentieth century there are associations dedicated to take care of people who suffer any mental disorder that make studies and research that help these people rejoin society.

The way men have been changing throughout history and the relationships between quality of life and technology development have been improved over time. "Besides the meeting place of technology and behavior, they are the link between household resources, the level of living, and the level of well-being" (Groot-Marcus, Terpstra, Steenbekkers, Butjijn, 2006).

The world is full of technology, and for better or worse, technology is with us every single minute of

our lives. This fact leads to both physical and mental illnesses and constantly to fields still unexplored by humans. Technology breakthroughs throw us into confusion when trying to define what well-being really is. This confusion results in the conception of products designed to “facilitate” people’s daily lives through the elimination of activities, rather than products designed for helping keep our mental health. “During the past decade, the role of technological objects in society and in people’s everyday lives has become a central theme in the philosophy of technology”. (Verbeek, 2006).

Generalized Anxiety Disorder in México

México is a country where it is evident that large cities can affect humans; according to the UN it has the fourth most populous city in the world. “The lifestyle of an individual actor is constructed from a series of building-blocks that relate to the sets of social practices and individual is involved in when enacting his or her daily life, together with the story-telling that goes along with it (Giddens, 1991).” Living in highly populated cities meant more traffic, a poor diet, longer work journeys to be within the competitiveness and hence implied the appearance of more physical and mental disorders.

“One in four people in Mexico has had at least one mental disorder and one in three people have had a mental disease at age 65, according to the study Psychiatric Disorders in Mexico : prevalence throughout life in a national representative sample study, published in 2007, is the latest compilation of statistical data at the population level in the country.” (Juarez, 2013).

Anxiety is along with depression one of the mental disorders that afflicts more people in the world. The Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD) has been described in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders of the American Psychiatric Association (APA) is a disorder that affects millions of people worldwide, but is more common in the cities than in villages or communities.

For 10 years now, studies have been alarming; according to the National Psychiatric epidemiology Survey, coordinated by the Dra. Maria Elena Medina Mora in Mexico, and raised in 2003, the most common disorders identified in our country were anxiety (with a prevalence of 14.3% ever the lives of the people) Newspaper Excelsior, 16- July- 2013).

That is why this project tries to flow with the times and support new generations living under the shadow of mental diseases by designing products and services that include them in society. These days have an increasing need to generate designs that promote well-being to face the problems of large cities.

Today it is imperative to pay attention to our lifestyle and find alternatives to this fast-paced world; objects have always had a symbolic value, as result of the experiences that people give them. They are filled with memories and experiences and are able to function as sensory time machines, able of trigger the senses

Figure 1.

positively or negatively.

Designing for people living with Anxiety Disorder

This project aims to bring design to people who suffer and live every day with mental disorders, specifically with Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD) and Panic Disorder.

This project is based on three stages:

1. My Covachita: The well-being at home
2. My Covachita: The well-being outside the home
3. My Covachita: The well-being in large cities

Which is the meaning of “Covachita”?

According to the Royal Academy of the Spanish Language (RAE), Covacha is 1. f. small cave. 2. f. housing or poor, uncomfortable, dark, small room. 3. f. storage room. 4. f. doghouse. 5. f. Ec. shop where you sell groceries.

There is a particular gesture in which we tend to do “Covachita” or “house” with our hands to protect something. This project was born because of that feeling, the need to feel safe.

Anxiety Disorder tends to have various symptoms, one of them is to feel exposed; that’s why the project tried to simulate the sensation of being safe and protected regardless if you are at home, outside the home, or in a large city.

My Covachita: The well-being at home

It is a cabinet that reflects harmony, lightness, simplicity and balance (Figure 1). These values are inspired by the simple lifestyle that exists in many communities and villages around Mexico and the world. It proposes to build furniture that has significance within the home and that denotes its impact on the physical and mental well-being through shapes and materials such as wood, textiles and mud.

Figure 2.

My Covachita: The well-being outside the home

Jewelry as an area of intervention is a logical approach in this project thanks to its natural ability to be carried by men thus having direct and constant contact with their bodies and sensory attention. The second approach involved in this project is made by two pieces of jewelry, a ring and a necklace (Figure 2). This family of objects will be able to accompany the person in their transits through the city.

Both ring and necklace have storage space; the first one for carrying an emergency pill with you. Second piece, necklace will help with a natural way of relaxing which is the aromatherapy.

My Covachita: The well-being at the cities

Street furniture is designed to be part of large cities in México such as México City, Guadalajara, and

Monterrey among others, and to be present when a person needs a break (Figure 3). Today it becomes imperative to look for new ways to develop our society; this could encompass what has not been made yet in socio- cultural democratization and therefore is not reflected in the collective behavior.

Conclusions

There are several different types of anxiety disorders, nowadays most of them are treated with therapy and pharmacological treatment. There are many alternative therapies that offer help to calm the mind and help society to live a peaceful life. We have to look for options both alternative and conventional.

Objects have always had a symbolic value as result of the experiences that people give them. They are filled with memories and experiences and are able to

Figure 3.

function as a time machine that contains information that activate the senses positively or negatively.

The project: Design for people living with mental disorders: Anxiety-My "Covachita", well-being for everybody is still in process. We need more test about our proposals inside different kind of groups; this is a first step to involve design in mental health and well-being.

Human behavior plays an important role in each period framed by history. Observation, registration, evaluation and interpretation of societies constitute the basic work to understand, disseminate and show the needs and problems that must be solved through design.

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Reconsidering education in retail design: Today's challenges and objectives

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Abstract Technology and digital developments are important drivers for new challenges and opportunities in retail, but also cause change in customers' shopping behaviour. Assuming these changes also affect the discipline of retail design and retail designers, the presented paper explores retail design as it is considered today from the perspective of practitioners and academics in the field. In this context, we propose two emerging challenges in coping with the prevailing developments which influence the discipline of retail design. We determined a lack of understanding the impact of ongoing phenomena on the retail designer and on their future requirements. Furthermore, we recognized a lack of specialized retail design courses which prepare future designers for this challenging field. The authors conclude with elucidating the context of ongoing research, which aims at overcoming current challenges.

Keywords Retail design, Education, Design process, Digitalisation, Omnichannel

Retail, omnichannel and the phygital space

Technological innovations have always been a driver for change in retail design. The invention of the escalator late 19th century, created a multilevel shop experience and the application of the barcode around 1950 made a larger shop space and product range possible (Quartier, 2011). Of more recent times are the global adoption of the internet and its commercial exploitation, causing the rise of e-commerce. Consequently, retailers are challenged to create a consistent brand story in the physical and online world.

From the customer's viewpoint; e-commerce, the access to information on the web and the rise of mobile technology have changed their shopping behaviour. Customers are becoming hyper-connected (Euromonitor, 2015) and according to Rigby (2014) digital technology has influenced the way they discover, evaluate, purchase, receive, use and return their products. Hence, retailers have started to change their strategies. A first example are the efforts of retailers and designers in differentiating the physical store from online and/or offline competitors by means of evoking memorable customer experiences (Petermans, Janssens, & Van Cleempoel, 2013). Second, retailers are expanding their commercial channels through which customers can interact with the firm, called multichannel (Neslin et al., 2006). More recently, retailers are now shifting to an omni-channel strategy, aiming at channel integration. Consequently, customers can use the channels interchangeable and seamlessly during the buying process (Verhoef, Kannan, & Inman, 2015). Starbucks' digital application for example, enables customers to pre-order, pay, collect rewards, and tip the barista by using their smartphone.

Omnichannel is driven and realised through new

technology and software (Brynjolfsson et al., 2013). Therefore, retailers rely on advanced technologies as a way to break down the barriers between the online/offline world (Brynjolfsson, Hu, & Rahman, 2013). In the store this technology is translated in applications such as virtual and interactive screens/mirrors, digital signage, mobile applications for product reviews or payment, etc. (Brynjolfsson et al., 2013; Piotrowicz & Cuthbertson, 2014).

The past few years, omnichannel has become a buzzword in retail, hence it is gaining more attention from the academic field. Building on multichannel inquiry (Verhoef et al., 2015), research in omnichannel is conducted from multiple angles such as retailing, marketing, business management & strategy, information system research, logistics, pervasive computing, etc. (Lazaris & Vrechopoulos, 2014; Picot-Coupey, Huré, Piveteau, Towers, & Kotzab, 2016).

In general, we noted that omnichannel research is mainly considered from the retailer's and/or customer's perspective or focusses on the technological aspect. Picot-Coupey (2016) for example thoroughly uncovers a firm's challenges during the development of the omnichannel strategy, but only addresses the retailer's experience. What stays unaddressed are the obstacles or opportunities during the creating of these *phygital* spaces from the creative executors' perspective, namely the retail design agency. Yet, like previous innovations, we presume that current changes also affect the practitioners' retail design thinking and doing. Samsung's new flagship store (New York) for example, reflects a change in the design and the purpose of the store to a digitally enabled, social, interactive and inspirational branded place. Given this gradual shift in the appearance and purpose of the physical store and its increasing digital connectedness; we assume future retail designers'

knowledge and skills will be even more challenged. In what follows, we will explore retail design as it is considered today by academics and professionals in the field. Ensuing on these arguments, we will discuss why retail design and design education need to be reconsidered in the light of current transitions.

The holistic turn in retail design

Retail design is a young evolving discipline (Christiaans & Almendra, 2012; Petermans & Van Cleempoel, 2010), often considered as a sub-discipline of interior design (Quartier, 2015; Skjulstad, 2014). The latter is rather logical, since the design of commercial spaces traditionally has belonged to the scope of interior designers (and architects) (Christiaans & Almendra, 2012). Driven by the emancipation of interior design in the '80 (Quartier, 2015), retail design has evolved from a rather artistic and interior-led discipline to a mature strategic, multi-disciplinary and customer-centric practice. Nowadays, the focus is on the functional aspects and commerciality, brand communication and the creation of experiences (Christiaans & Almendra, 2012; Dalziel, 2014; Quartier, 2015; van Tongeren, 2013). Hence, Quartier (2015), Skjulstad (2014) and Christiaans & Almendra (2012), desire to acknowledge retail design as an independent discipline. Arguing that retail design goes beyond aesthetic and functional design of a space, they point out that it embraces multiple disciplines such as interior design, architecture, product design, graphic design and needs to be further substantiated with knowledge from social sciences (e.g. psychology and sociology), service design, communication, branding theory and marketing. Thereupon, Quartier (2015) defines retail design as the design of spaces for selling products/or services and/or brands to consumers. Besides, it is interdisciplinary in order to create a sensory interpretation of brand values, through physical or virtual stores. The definition still echoes the relatedness with interior design as it involves the design of the physical space. However, the virtual space has now been brought forward as belonging to the scope of retail design. Supporting this notion, Christiaans & Almendra (2012) claim to be aware of the technological developments in retail design. In their conviction, advanced technology allows for new ways of interacting and demand reconsidering the physical and virtual space in terms of what both spaces and products are, their function and how they are used and experienced (Christiaans & Almendra, 2012). Concerning the digital, aspect David Dalziel (2014), head of London based retail design agency Dalziel & Pow, deems on it as a new tool for retail design which contributes to the customer's retail experience. Furthermore, he assumes digital design to become stronger and more integrated in the future. Yet, the growing pervasiveness of digital aspects in the built environment seem to imply a change in the role of future spatial designers. This was staded by Yildirim (2016) who did a survey with interior design students about their perception of smart pervasive domestic environments and their future role as designer. About 88% of the students expected a shift in their future roles. Additionally, students supposed creativity, technological, material and system design knowledge to become more important, together with

an increasing need for interdisciplinarity with fields as industrial design, psychology and computer engineering. Subsequently, Teufel & Zimmerman (2015), plea for a new generation of retail designers who approach the design process in a holistic way. They define holistic retail design as the creation of shopping experiences across stationary, temporary, digital customer touch-points and what shapes spaces, platforms, events, interfaces, signage and communications. The aim is to evoke attention, reputation and customer loyalty for retail brands. In the context of holistic retail design, the authors suggest there is a need for designers who have a thorough understanding of all retail parameters. Besides, they need to think and work on the level of communications, graphics, space and the digital sphere (Teufel & Zimmermann, 2015).

In sum, these statements illustrate the field's desire to evolve towards an independent and distinctive discipline. Furthermore, it reflects the specific interdisciplinary character of retail design which originates from the complex and fast evolving field of retail, the changing customer's needs and technological developments in our society.

Regarding the retail designer's role, the findings reflect a need for practitioners whose knowledge goes beyond the creation of functional and aesthetic store environments. Based on the perceived changing strategies and digital developments in retail, we suggest future retail designers should be able to transform a retailer's omnichannel marketing aspirations into a strategic and creative phygital design.

In the context of the aforementioned transitions in retail design, we identified two challenges concerning the retail designer and retail design education. First, from the retail designer's perspective we noticed a knowledge gap in terms of understanding the impact of ongoing phenomena on their design process and their future requirements (skills, attitude and knowledge). We conducted a review of professional literature, written by retail design practitioners. We selected literature that essentially dealt with practical guidelines to develop commercial environments. The review showed that the shared practitioner's knowledge mainly addresses the components of the physical environment and overlooks the digital aspect and the growing number of retail channels. Authors who did touch themes as the changing character of retail, omnichannel and digitalisation were rather vague by recommending to approach the commercial concept in a holistic, consistent and coherent way (e.g. van Tongeren, 2013).

Second, regarding the retail designer's training, we determined a minor presence of specialized retail design courses on master, bachelor and postgraduate level. Courses are mainly approached as a part of the interior design training. This despite of the fact that the academic field echoes for retail design to become a discipline in its own right (e.g. Quartier, 2015) and to broaden the discipline's body of knowledge (Petermans & Van Cleempoel, 2010). Therefore, we hope current

Figure 1. Retail interior design process model .

examples such as the master training at Piet Zwart Institute in Rotterdam and the recent new bachelor program at Westerdals School of Arts, Communication and Technology in Oslo (see Skjulstad, 2015) to be encouraging drivers for future retail design education.

To conclude, as we believe that research in the designer's field of activity and retail design education are beneficial to overcome these current challenges, we conclude this paper with our objective for further research.

Objective for further research

The presented paper aimed at outlining prevailing

tensions and challenges in the field of retail design caused by the current developments in retail, the changing customer and increasing digitalisation. Therefore, we wish to position this paper in the context of ongoing PhD research. We aim at overcoming the field's challenges by means of opening up the actual notion of the discipline of retail design and to focus on retail design education. The overall research project follows four major phases. **First**, we want to grasp the discipline's current body of knowledge and way of working. This implies understanding the retail design process and the characteristics of today's retail designers in terms of knowledge, skills and attitude. **Second**, as we have

mapped the prevailing developments in retail driven by technological and digital advancements, we want to understand the impact on the retail design discipline from the perspective of the retail designer. Questions that will be addressed in this matter are: do today's retail designers experience specific challenges in the execution of the strategic and creative design process? Do they experience knowledge gaps or lack in skills regarding the rise of pervasive technology in the retail environment and omnichannel in retail? What are the requirements and the desired role of future retail designers? **Third**, as academics and practitioners suggest a holistic approach in retail design, we want to grasp how this is done in practice. Therefore, we will rely on best practice examples, namely retail design agencies that execute the design process in a holistic way. Concretely, this means that they translate a retailer's omnichannel aspirations into a commercial concept which covers all channels. **Fourth**, as the research exerts a top-down approach, findings from the field will serve to reconsider the way current retail designers are trained. They form the starting point in our reflection of developing a conceptual *ideal* retail design program which meets the requirements of future practitioners.

Currently, we are in the first phase of the project in which we have developed a conceptual model, representing a retail interior design process (Figure 1). The model is derived from a review of professional retail design literature combined with academic perspectives on retail design and the design process. This led to the composition of a visual model which reflects the design process, supplemented with related (design) activities and tools. Furthermore, the model shows the complex intertwining of the retailer, the retail designer and society in which the customer is embedded. Moreover, the model reflects the changing and complex character of the design process. Illustrated as connected shapes, the model suggests the never ending design process (Doyle, 2004; van Tongeren, 2013) and refers to the ongoing developments in the field caused by changes in society which affect retail and vice versa (Murialdo, 2013; van Tongeren, 2013).

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Familiarity vs ambiguity: Exploring the potentials of ambiguity in user interface design

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Abstract In this paper the importance of using familiarity vs ambiguity in design and the possible implications of applying ambiguity in product design are explored and discussed. Because of recent technological developments and the increase of interactive products, user interfaces have become more ambiguous for certain users. Smart devices stretch the context in which the products are usually used. With help from research in other fields, the appeal of ambiguity is explored and the relevance for the field of design is explained. Our conclusion is that ambiguity can be beneficial for users especially for providing novel and exciting experiences, yet some users will not be able to tolerate ambiguity. Designers should therefore handle ambiguity with care. Thus, they can aim to design familiar yet ambiguous interfaces to keep the balance between ease of use and highly affective product experience.

Keywords *Ambiguity, Familiarity, Metaphors, User interfaces, Product design*

Introduction

Human Computer Interaction has increased over the last 15 years due to the development of personal devices like smartphones, tablets and computers, significantly changing the way people interact with products (Harvard Business Review, 2014 and Emarketer, 2015). Consequently, the way that the user interfaces (UIs) of these products were designed became increasingly important. As a consequence of these technological developments, a visual language needed to be created for products that users were not familiar with. With the designers' design space foremost dominated by ambiguous shapes that represent computer functions, there was an urgency to present the virtual shapes in a more familiar way to the users. As a result, ambiguity has been avoided in UI designs and instead familiar objects were chosen to signify a function in a digital platform (e.g., see Figure 1 for the image of a trash bin representing the function of deleting digital files (see also Gaver, 1989)). However, this paper discusses the current needs in UI design and its relevance for ambiguity.

Familiar yet Ambiguous?

The tendency to facilitate ease of use by adding familiar elements within the design of UI is not strange. Research on familiarity revealed that repeated exposure to a certain stimulus makes people like this

stimulus better (Bornstein, 1989; Zajonc, 1968, 1980). This process is referred to in literature as mere exposure effect (MEE), which can both occur when individuals are consciously aware of stimuli as well as unconsciously (Bornstein, 1989). Familiar objects also have the capacity to elicit a mental model in users which encompass previous experiences with the object and conceptually and contextually relevant knowledge. Similarly, mental models and knowledge adhering to an object should shape and affect behaviour (Marks & Olson, 1981). That is, as users have been already repeatedly exposed to daily objects and have familiarity with them, seeing known objects on User Interfaces creates a sense of comfort and safety while navigating through the product.

One way to achieve familiarity and subsequently facilitate ease of use is through the use of metaphors. Metaphors are defined in contemporary theories as *a structuring of our cognitive system* (Lakoff, 1987; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). That means that metaphors have their effect on the way we perceive the world as well as how we categorize experiences and organize our thoughts (Casakin, 2007). Metaphors are valuable for designers in a sense that it could enable them to understand unfamiliar design problems by juxtaposing them with known situations. Metaphors might have a fundamental role as they are said to

Figure 1. The evolution of the recycle bin in Microsoft's Windows operating system through the years.

Figure 2. The Fonckel one, a LED luminaire that brings together multi – touch sensing, and our human bodily and emotional experience. The user can control the light of the luminaire by making gestures on the multi – touch surface on the back. The gestures needed to operate the light make use of metaphors. That means, waking up the light is done by making an upward gesture over back of the luminaire, where after the light will follow your hand. When you want to broaden the light, you simply make a stretching gesture on the back of the luminaire, for a more focussed light you pinch. With this the LED luminaire enables people to shape light almost as if they can grab it directly with their hands, making it their own personalized expression. (Studio Philip Ross, 2015).

guide reasoning and enhance innovative thinking. Subsequently allowing the designer to think unconventionally as well as encouraging the implementation of novel ideas to design problems (Casakin, 2007). Therefore, metaphors are instrumental for designers and users of UIs, enabling designers to make the abstract understandable by means of evoking familiarity. Consequently making the introduction of a complex technology bearable for novel users.

Nowadays the once complex technologies are properly integrated in the daily life of most modern societies. Users have more experience with using UIs found in their tablets, phones, refrigerators, game consoles, home heating control systems. Therefore with metaphors, designers have more liberty to use form that resembles less and less the source object to represent the targeted function or desired message through abstraction techniques (Cila, 2013). In addition to that, interaction with technology starts early in childhood – the present generation of computers users are often referred to as digital natives - making the need for familiarity no longer essential. For children everything is ambiguous at a certain stage in their life because their brain operates continuously at this unstable state - are thus far better equipped to learn to use novel, unclear interactions. This is in contrast with the elderly of today who often resort to what they know about familiar objects, because it is safe. One could argue that the transition period between the non – digital age and the digital age is over for younger generations since digital natives have already adapted to digital systems.

It is particularly interesting to see how UI designs will change over the years with the digital natives as the future users, because UIs are not only limited to the functional digital products anymore. Certain ‘crossover’ accessories have made their entrance into contemporary home environments (smart lamps,

Figure 3. Philips’ HUE system, which allows users to adjust the lighting characteristics of light sources (intensity and colour temperature) through their smartphone. The system allows the user to control all lighting sources in home through the use of an app, meaning that you do not have to switch on each luminaire individually. It even allows users to schedule different lighting settings through the course of a day or let the system change the lighting dynamically. It furthermore allows users to change the characteristics of light source individually, making that the interaction with the product differs from the interaction you have with ordinary light sources. (Philips, 2015).

interactive walls and interactive tables). For example, the Fonckel One designed by Studio Philip Ross (see in Figure 2) and the Philips HUE system (see in Figure 3), from which the interaction is different in comparison to ordinary lighting sources. These emerging product categories will probably be commonplace in future households, seemingly making a meaningful addition to the furniture that people already own, however raising the question if creating full familiarity is still a necessity for these products; or whether there are other ways to make the use of metaphors more intriguing.

One could even argue that some of the metaphors that were meant to evoke familiarity in UIs have lost their connection to the real world, at least for some users. This is best demonstrated by looking at the future generations of product users: the children of today. To some extent everything is ambiguous for children, since they learn about the context of products when they grow up. It is interesting that children growing up in the coming years will come across certain app icons (for instance) from which they know the consequences - they *know* what will happen when they tap the icon - but they will not understand *why* the interaction they have to make with the application is shaped the way it is. For example, the ‘call’ option on your phone still uses the archetypical phone to indicate its purpose and some archetypical characteristics. Most children growing up right

now have probably never seen an old fashioned phone (at home) that is similar to this archetypical phone, so it is not possible for them to make the connection between the interaction and the actual purpose of the product. More examples of the same issue could be found, for example the floppy disk – shaped save button in MS Word.

It may seem as if consciously incorporating familiarity through metaphors has lost its purpose over time, however the opposite is true. Using obvious metaphors referring to archaic principles is instrumental in retaining involvement of the elderly users of digital systems. However, in such cases familiarity is often retained through analogical references (i.e., seeing an analogue phone horn indicates 'call' function). When the source for the metaphor and the target function are conceptually very closely related, identification of the function in UI is cognitively rather easy and affectively not so intriguing (Cila, Özcan & Hekkert, 2012). Understanding the interaction needed to use the product without having metaphors (AKA analogies, in this case) that create familiarity, could prove to be rather difficult and even dissatisfactory due to inconsistencies between expectations and reality (Anderson & Jolson, 1973).

This creates a certain dilemma for designers; although there is valid foundation for using analogies and metaphors for creating familiarity, using them might also be redundant or even limiting to the experience products can offer to users. Analogies could be limiting since it has been asserted that familiarity hinders creativity and even critical thinking. Novelty on the other hand and some level of ambiguity can create more exciting interfaces (Hekkert et al, 2003). Designers aim to provide users with rich experiences through the product design (e.g., evoking positive emotions as well as negative emotions through design, Fokkinga, & Desmet, 2012). If metaphors are used cleverly, they can also create rather rich experiences because they create duality in meaning attribution (Hekkert & Cila, 2015). Similarly, across the fields of design, arts and literature ambiguity, as well, is seen as a source for providing users with rich experiences. According to Gaver, Beaver and Benford (2003, p. 1) because an ambiguous object is "*intriguing, mysterious and delightful. It leaves space for people's own interpretation encouraging them to play with concepts and their context, which eventually will establish a more personal relation with the meaning offered by those systems.*" Taking part in the meaning making process could be important since this creates a sense of achievement and satisfaction for users.

Why ambiguity works

It is interesting to explore *why* embedding ambiguity in designs across all disciplines is regarded as a worthwhile choice despite the possibility of excluding certain users (e.g., elderly or culturally different users). In other fields, (e.g., different fields of art and politics), advances are made with exploring the reasons of people to favour ambiguity. It is interesting to see whether insights found in these fields of study are applicable to product design.

A study led by psychologist Claudia Muth in which participants were asked to evaluate paintings, showed that when the perceived degree of ambiguity was higher within an artwork, the higher the appreciation was of the participants for the artwork. Participants explained their higher appreciation with the argumentation that they found the ambiguous artworks more interesting and affecting. However, the

research revealed that 'figuring out' the meaning of an art piece was not linked to this pleasure. The research showed that a work's solvability was in no way connected to the liking of the painting and negatively linked to interest and emotional involvement. Therefore, the researchers claimed that: "*A complete resolution of ambiguity is not necessary for the appreciation of an artwork.*" (Muth, Hesslinger & Carbon, 2015).

Another study exploring the importance of ambiguity in relation to the human brain argued the following: The human brain operates close to an unstable point, as revealed by synergetics (Fuller, 1975) and the theory of complexity (BusinessDictionary, 2015). Argued is that the human brain can only create new forms of behaviour when operating close to criticality. Hence ambiguity in art should be considered as an important tool, because ambiguity is according to the researchers in particular suited to keep the brain near this unstable, critical state (Yevin, 2006).

Based on the insights gained from research to ambiguity in fields other than product design can be argued that there is a valid foundation for using ambiguity. Not for the sole reason of enjoyment of ambiguity, but rather for its apparent indispensable ability to keep the brain within an unstable state, receptive to new stimuli which are essential for continued creation and learning.

Conclusion

By exploring the relevance of ambiguity and familiarity in UI design, it became apparent that there are some merits to both principles. Familiarity is essential for making UIs that can be understood by any user. Metaphors, as well as analogies, play an instrumental role in achieving familiarity since they play a role in the way we perceive the world and frame our experiences. Metaphors furthermore facilitate designers in their desire to solve design problems, because metaphors can enhance innovative thinking and thereby help designers to implement novel ideas to design problems. However, the general opinion from a designer's perspective is that with the help of ambiguity designers can offer users richer product experiences and the interactions that people have with products can stretch beyond the expectations of the users leaving space for intrigue, excitement, and sense of discovery.

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iGuide - A new way for discovering tourist hotspots with children

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Abstract This paper describes the iGuide, a new device that will help families to have a pleasant and interesting tour in the city of Curitiba (Brazil), going from one attraction to another while having fun. The iGuide is in the shape of a magnifying glass that uses a hologram to show information about tourist hotspots, maps and important places that the family may need during the tour. The children will be the ones using the device and they are going to be the guides for their families. In this way they would not get bored or bother their parents during the tour. The device brought a new way of exploring the city.

Keywords *Conceptual product, Emotional design, Children, Tourism*

Introduction

Curitiba, the capital of Paraná, is a beautiful city for families to visit. Parks, museums and important monuments are a “must see”. The city hall has a sightseeing bus tour that, just like every tourist bus, takes the visitors from one attraction to another. Even though Curitiba is a big city, many tourist hotspots are very close to each other and it is possible to walk from one to another, instead of getting on the bus for just a short drive. That is why the iGuide was developed. The iGuide is a conceptual product, a magnifying glass that will help families to have an interesting tour that provides information about the tourist places without getting lost. The most interesting part of this system is that children will be responsible for handling it, becoming the guides of the tour.

Theoretical basis

The need to understand the emotional aspects presented in human interactions with products is essential in the field of design. In this sense, emotional design aims to identify and understand features related to the perception and cognition of the individual towards objects.

Objects are able to influence the occurrence of certain emotions, affecting the process of the design. As Desmet (In: SUSAGROUP, 2015) claims, emotions are part of human nature and everything in the world has a constant influence on them. Therefore, it is impossible to ignore the emotional side of product experience; it would be like denying that products are designed, bought and used by humans.

The emotional design theory (Norman, 2004) presents a model of design with three levels. These levels affect the relations that individuals have with objects, combining both cognition and emotions. The visceral

level is concerned with appearances and it is not culturally dependent. The behavioural level is to do with product usability. The reflective level considers the status given by the product. These three levels of design motivated Norman to state that “aesthetically beautiful objects enable you to work better”.

In the design process, it is also important to analyse those levels in order to have a design capable of reaching the users’ desires. Löbach (1976) argues that the industrial designer must meet the multiple needs and aspirations of users and user groups, in order to provide the product with the appropriate functions for each case.

Desmet and Hekkert (2007) claim that “the emerging interest in user-centred design has stimulated a shift of focus from the users’ behaviour and cognition to the users’ affective experience of (and involvement in) the human-product interaction”. The authors distinguish three components of a product experience: aesthetic pleasure, attribution of meaning and emotional response.

The aesthetic experience is considered to be the product’s capacity to delight the sensory modalities, related to the shape, the colours, the sounds and the touch. The experience of meaning is related to cognition and its processes such as interpretation, memory retrieval and associations, where people can assess the symbolic significance of products. At the emotional level, Desmet and Hekkert (2007) refer to the affective phenomena considered in emotion psychology about emotions, love and disgust, fear and desire etc. The emotions are functional, establishing the position towards certain people, objects, actions and ideas. The development of this conceptual project was based on these concepts.

Figures 1 and 2. Digital mock-up of the iGuide and a detail of the "Next" button.

Methodology

The literature review helped to structure the concept of the product and it was based on Löbach's (1976) four stages of product development, which are: problem analysis, problem solutions, evaluation of problem solutions and realization of problem solution. However, the last stage was not considered as the product was a digital mock-up. The device's creative name came from the Technique Methodology developed by Nöllke (2010) and it is called Brainwriting. It consists of collecting as many names as possible in a very quick way, without judging if they are good or not. This is a very interesting and effective way to choose a good name for a project or device.

The conceptual product

Aims

The main idea for the project was to develop a system to help tourists get from one attraction to another in Curitiba, without worrying about getting lost. The development of the project started with some references of the Van Gogh Museum in Amsterdam (Holland), where children have some assignments during a visit with their parents, so they do not get bored and still have fun. This system could be motivating if combined with the idea of tourism for families in Curitiba.

The product took the shape of a magnifying glass so that the children would have an interesting object in their hands. The interaction would make the children feel important while guiding their family to the right place. The iGuide was developed to stimulate a new and different way to tour Curitiba.

Physical construction

The magnifying glass was designed to be 32cm in

length, with a circumference of 15cm, 1.5cm thick, and it has a string to tie to onto the child's wrist or rest round their neck (Figures 1 and 2). This object was made of acrylic, since it is very likely that it could fall to the ground. The circumference was translucent because it changes colour according to the way the family is going. The colour would be green if the user was going in the right way, or red if the user was going the wrong way. This system would work by being integrated with a GPS.

Use and features

The user would get the device from the bus driver as soon as they enter a bus. The first hologram would appear showing the instructions (Figures 3 and 4).

The magnifying glass has the whole route planned out and is operated using a GPS system. In order to go from one main tourist attraction to another, it would show other places on the way that were near to each other, guiding the family in the right direction. Supposing the family started their tour at the Oscar Niemeyer Museum and they had already finished the visit, the child would press the "Next" button to see the next point they had to look for. In this case, it would be Rio Iguaçu Square, which is easy to find, since it is very close to the museum. It would appear for only five seconds but, in case the child forgets or does not see it, it was possible to press the "Next" button again and the same hologram would be shown. They would walk until they found Rio Iguaçu Square and when they were nearby, the green light that was already on (since they had started to walk) would start to blink, indicating that they were close. It was time for the child to get into action and point the magnifying glass at the attraction, as if he or she were taking a picture. If the device recognised the place it would stop blinking and show a small text with information about it, also as a hologram. The child could read the

Figures 3 and 4. Instruction screens and hologram of the map.

Figure 5. Route from Oscar Niemeyer Museum to Passeio Público.

information out loud, presenting the details to the parents, feeling like a real guide. When the family was ready and wanted to move on, the child would press the “Next” button and the hologram for the next point would appear.

The next tourist spot could be seen from the Square so there was no way to get lost and if the child started walking in the wrong direction the green light would turn red, meaning that it was better to go back. In case the family did not find the right street, the device was prepared to guide them to the right path. By pressing the “Map” button a map would appear as a hologram, indicating where the family was and where they had to go (the tourist attraction they were looking for). The indicator would move as the family walked, so it is very easy to get back on track. When they got to the right attraction, the hologram would disappear automatically.

They could use three different buttons if they had some other special needs during the trip, “Bus” (green), “Food” (red) and “Toilet” (yellow). If anyone needed any of those options, they would press the button and a map would appear showing where the nearest option was. When the family was ready they could turn it on again by pressing the “Next” button to see where they should go, or the “Map” button, to help them get back on the right path.

Figure 5 shows an infographic of the route from the Oscar Niemeyer Museum to Passeio Público. The route illustrates only a small part of the city but it could be extended to other tourist attractions.

Logo

The main concern for the “iGuide” brand’s logo was to create a visual symbolism that could transmit the curious ambiguity of the letter “i”. It was decided to use “iGuide” because of the fun that the word could involve: “Eye Guide” and “iGuide” have the same pronunciation. However, they have different meanings. Some of the alternatives for the logo are shown in Figure 6. The colours chosen recall the colours of the Brazilian flag, green, yellow, blue and white.

Framework of product experience

Based on the framework of product experience by Desmet and Hekkert (In: Green and Jordan, 2002), it was possible to allocate the design of the iGuide at the levels proposed.

The aesthetic experience was considered in the design to develop a product, in this case, a magnifying glass, able to delight the sensory modalities: an interesting object with the idea of bringing the concept of discovering the city, with colours that could change according to the way people made the choice for the tour. The interface would also provide an enjoyable way to interact by using aesthetic features.

The experience of meaning was related to the interpretation and associations, where people could assess the symbolic significance of products. In this sense, using the iGuide, the children would present the details to their parents, impersonating a real tour guide. The parents would also be glad to give their children the power to show them the information about the sightseeing spots.

At the emotional level, this interaction would provide both parents and children with a pleasant experience that could be remarkable in many ways, bringing emotions such as pleasure and joy. The children would believe that they were in charge and the parents would be glad that their children would also be enjoying the trip.

Considerations

Tourism in Curitiba is an excellent programme for families and checking out all the tourist hotspots could be more interesting and efficient with the iGuide, the magnifying glass that could help families to get from one place to another.

The idea and concept were innovative and could attract more people to take the tourist buses and could, in the future, be a possibility for creating a new form of tourism for the city. The families could have a better experience discovering Curitiba in a different way. The project could inspire other kinds of devices

Figure 6. Alternatives for the logo.

or objects for tourists to explore the beauty of the city of Curitiba and other cities as well.

This project was carried out during a Conceptual Design course. This was part of the internationalisation process of the Federal University of Technology – Parana. It was offered in English and the students were from the Design course. They were not concerned with technical and economic issues so it gave them a great deal of freedom to create an interactive product where the emotions played a bigger role during the development process than the usual process. This approach was able to embrace new ways of interpreting and developing design.

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The influence of context in subjective impressions. A case study on the influence of decoration styles in consumer's subjective impressions ceramic flooring

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Abstract Materials perception plays an important role in the subjective impressions (meanings and emotions) that a product can elicit. New research activity to systematically explore the relationship between the attributes of materials and subjective experiences of their multisensory perception is been carried out in the last decade. This paper contributes in this aim providing a two phase study about the impact that the context, through three different decoration styles, has on the subjective impressions evoked by a particular ceramic floor, showed through computer renderings. In the first phase, semantic differential technique was used on a 70 participant on-line survey, whereas a combination of semantic differential and eye-tracking techniques was used in the second phase with 30 participants. Results of the first phase showed that the used decoration styles can influence certain subjective impressions related to the material. This was confirmed by the second experimental study where besides, eye-tracking techniques have also showed some differences in gaze behavior depending on the context, and between women and men.

Keywords *Decoration influence, Ceramic flooring, Eye-tracking, Semantic differential, Subjective impressions*

Introduction

Consumer preferences and behavior have long been a topic of interest for researchers in many disciplines, such as product design, engineering, marketing, or psychology (Veryzer, 2005; Seva, Duh and Helander, 2007). As investigation techniques evolve, new methodologies are developed that can be applied to determine the exact factors that influence consumer decisions. In an era where product functional requirements are regularly met, designers strive to understand the consumer needs located at the highest level of the Jordan's hierarchy (Jordan, 2000), i.e. the subjective impressions (meanings and emotions) that a product can elicit.

Different strategies can be used to measure the meaning and emotions evoked by a product or environment. The Semantic differential technique (Osgood, Suci and Tannenbaum, 1957) is based on product semantics and relies on product assessments using Likert scales with antonym expressions. This is a standard tool to elicit subjective perception about products (Chang and Wu, 2009; Cheng and Chang, 2009).

However, new alternatives in evaluation techniques have been incorporated in design practice in the last years. One of them is the use of neuro-technologies to investigate perception and evoked emotions combined

with semantics measures (Rojas et al., 2015; Piqueras-Fiszman et al., 2013). These new synergies provide a new way to analyze the emotional impact of design, and put aside the speculation of affective process.

Eye-Tracking is a powerful technique to analyze gaze behavior and attention (Rayner, 1998). When we read, look at a scene, or search for an object, we make continuous eye movements called saccades. Important variables can be obtained from these actions. Movement and attention require spending time on the stimulus. These elements are the basis of a number of methods used to filter visual information. Eye movements provide an objective indicator of where a person's overt attention (and usually also their covert) is focused (Hoffman and Subramaniam, 1995; Spence and Driver, 2004). Although several aspects of oculomotor behavior can be used, the locus of an observer's visual fixations is perhaps the single most commonly used parameter when it comes to assessing where a consumer's attention might be focused (Piqueras-Fiszman et al., 2013).

The connection between visual elements and their psychological effects has been a topic under active discussion (Moszkowicz, 2011). Research shows that gaze can capture elements that may psychologically and physiologically influence the observer, as our eyes are connected to emotions and attention can be biased

Figure 1. The four images used in the pilot study. Image d was only used in this phase. Images a, b and c were used in the second phase.

by mood (Joormann and Gotlib, 2007; Kellough, Beevers, Ellis and Wells, 2008). Emotional and cognitive processes can be measured relatively accurately with eye-tracking technology, even when participants are sitting in front of a computer screen (Liu, Lai and Chuang, 2011). Recording gaze data can help us understand judgments related to specific design attributes.

In this paper, we try to explore how our perception of materials is influenced by different decoration styles. Using a case study, we try to assess the impressions evoked by a particular ceramic floor using both subjective techniques (semantic differential) and objective ones (eye-tracking). In both cases we use computer renderings as stimuli to get user perceptual responses. Some products such as furniture or floorings, are widely displayed through renders on internet pages, in advertising, and even also through the stages of the design and development process. Virtual representations provide an interesting framework to experiment with new design alternatives (Söderman, 2005; Serrano, Botella, Baños, & Alcañiz, 2013) and current real time computer graphics technology can provide ultra-realistic renderings where it is difficult to distinguish between real and virtual representations. Regarding the virtual or real nature of the stimuli used to assess user perception, Söderman (2005) concludes that for efficient product evaluations with users there are other factors to consider than the degree of realism in the product representations. For example, that the participants are well familiar with the type of product, but also with the type of representation technology to be used. In other study (Artacho-Ramírez, Diego-Mas, & Alcaide-Marzal, 2008) regarding the realism of the representation, one of the conclusions was that there is a majority of concepts that the product is able to transmit in the same way independently of the type of representation.

Experimental work

Experimental work has been organized in two phases. In the first one, semantic differential was used on a pilot study where an on-line survey (with 70 participants) was used to ask participants about the

subjective impressions evoked by a particular ceramic flooring, presented through different images of a same room, but with different options of furniture and decorative elements (and also without furniture). In phase two, 30 subjects participated on a new study. This time participants' subjective impressions were again analyzed through semantic differential technique, and also their gaze over the ceramic flooring images were measured, using eye-tracking technology. Both studies used high quality computer generated renderings displayed on a computer screen as stimuli. The next sections describe in detail both experiments.

Phase 1: Pilot study

Image selection: ceramic flooring

The ceramic tile flooring was picked from the group of the highest ranked floors from a previous study on the subjective impressions elicited by ceramic tile floorings (Agost and Vergara, 2014). The original rendered image in that study was of a 'neutral' room, with no decorative elements (image "d" in Figure 1). Three other rendered images of the same room were generated, this time with furniture and elements of varied decoration styles. The furniture included a dining table and chairs, a couch, and other complementary elements (see images "a", "b" and "c" in Figure 1).

The same ceramic tile flooring was used in all four images. However, the three furnished ones are seen from a different camera angle from the one used in the original empty room image, where a window and two doors prevent from including the furniture. Consequently, results of the original empty room will be taken into consideration only in this phase of the study, for subjective impression.

Identification of subjective impressions

The selection of subjective impressions is based on the results of the previous study on ceramic flooring (Agost and Vergara, 2014). In that study, the 24 original semantic descriptors considered were reduced to 9 factors (pairs of antonym adjectives), applying factorial analysis. We have adopted these nine pairs of adjectives (see Table 1). Besides, in the cited study the 14 emotional descriptors were reduced to only one, which coincided with the preference. We have now included the emotion (preference) through the assertion "Like flooring". Two other pairs of assertions ("Like decorations"; "Decorations adequacy") regarding decoration preferences have been added, as we want to study decoration influence. The survey was conducted in Spanish (participants' first language) (see Table 1). Each pair of antonym assertions was further explained in the survey instructions.

Participants were asked to assess each pair of assertions using a 5-point Likert scale. During the analysis phase, the scale ratings were adjusted to -2 to +2. The first assertion in each pair corresponds to the highest value in the score.

Survey: participants and materials

The survey was conducted via on-line questionnaires.

Participants included university staff, their relatives, and acquaintances. Seventy responses were recorded (39 men and 31 women). Each participant was randomly assigned one of the four possible images (see Figure 1) and asked to assess the subjective impressions elicited by the ceramic flooring, by rating the scales of the pairs of assertions (Table 1). Thus, all participants were asked to assess the same ceramic flooring, regardless of the room decoration style assigned. Eighteen responses were recorded for image "a", 19 responses for image "b", 18 responses for image "c", and 15 responses for image "d".

Data analysis

First we have analyzed whether the responses of the 9 pairs of antonym adjectives, which represent the judgment of the floorings, affect the flooring preferences (the assertion "Like flooring") or even with the decoration preferences (the other two questions "Like decorations" and "Decorations adequacy"). To gain insight about these preferences, correlation coefficients were calculated between the responses of the 9 pairs of antonym adjectives shown in Table 1, and the pair of assertions showing preference: "Like flooring". Additional correlation coefficients were calculated between "Like flooring" and the other two questions about preferences: "Like decorations" and "Decorations adequacy". The Spearman coefficient was used, because the variables did not follow a normal distribution (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results revealed significant differences with normal distribution, $p < 0.05$, for all variables).

Second, we have analyzed whether the judgment of the floorings (adjective assessments) are influenced by the type of decoration, in order to conclude that decoration styles can influence subjective impressions of the floorings. As variables cannot be assumed to follow a normal distribution, Kruskal-Wallis tests were applied in order to check the influence of the type of decoration on the 11 assessments related to the subjective impressions evoked by the flooring (independent variable: type of decoration; dependent variables: assessment ratings to each pair of

assertions -subjective impressions-). When the Kruskal-Wallis test showed significant differences, the Mann-Whitney U test for two independent samples was applied. Bonferroni adjustment was considered in order to control the error rate (the probability of making type I errors). Since the four type of decoration need six pair comparisons (1-2, 1-3, 1-4, 2-3, 2-4, 3-4), Bonferroni adjustment leads to a critical significance level for the decision of $p = 0.05/6 = 0.0083$.

Results of pilot study

The Spearman correlation coefficients between the adjectives and the question about preference ("Like flooring") are shown in Table 2. It can be observed that only the adjectives with a symbolic meaning maintain a significant correlation with "Like flooring", while adjectives with a more functional meaning do not correlate with this assessment. This result agrees with the previous study (Agost and Vergara, 2014).

The Spearman correlation coefficients between "Like flooring" and the rest of preferences are shown in Table 3. Flooring preference is significantly correlated with a taste for the decorations, but it is not with the adequacy of the decorations. In other words, it seems reasonable to choose decorations based on subjective impressions, regardless of their adequacy for the specific type of flooring.

The Kruskal-Wallis test shows that significant differences (significance value $p < 0.05$) can be considered between types of decoration for some adjectives: "Versatile" (significance value $p = 0.41$), "Innovative" ($p < 0.001$), "Bright" ($p = 0.037$), and "Expensive looking" ($p = 0.037$). However, the subsequent application of the Mann-Whitney U test for two samples (taking critical significance level = 0.0083) shows that only significant difference is identified in the assessment of "Innovative" between decorations "a" and "b" ($p = < 0.001$) and between decoration "a" and image "d" ($p = 0.002$) (see Figure 2). Nevertheless, as it has been previously pointed, differences identified between a furnished image and image "d" will not be considered.

Table 1. Pairs of antonym assertions representing subjective impressions used in the pilot study.

Subjective Impressions		
(A: Adjective/ P: Preference)	Spanish words	Translation
A: Versatile	Sencillo, versatile/Recargado, poco adaptable	Simple, versatile/Excessively ornate, not adaptable
A: Innovative	Innovador/ Tradicional	Innovative / Traditional
A: Bright	Luminoso/ Apagado	Bright/Dark
A: Resistant	Resistente/ Frágil	Resistant/ Fragile
A: Easy to clean	Fácil limpieza/Difícil limpieza	Easy to clean/Difficult to clean
A: Cosy	Hogareño/ Poco domestico	Cosy/ Not cosy
A: Expensive	Aspecto de caro/ Aspecto barato	Expensive looking/ Cheap looking
A: Natural	Natural/ Artificial	Natural/ Artificial
A: Elegant	Elegante/Vulgar	Elegant/ Ordinary
P: Flooring	Me gusta el pavimento/ no me gusta	I like the flooring/ I do not like it
P: Decorations	Me gusta la decoración / No me gusta	I like decorations/ I do not like them
P: Decorations adequacy	El mobiliario y el resto de elementos decorativos son adecuados para el pavimento de la estancia: Muy adecuados/ Nada adecuados	The furniture and the rest of decorative elements are suitable for the room flooring: Very appropriate/ Not suitable

In this particular case, the decoration style used can influence the assessment of the floor innovation. Results of this pilot study show that the decoration style used can influence certain subjective impressions related to the flooring.

Therefore, it was decided to perform a second phase of the study. This time the aim was applying the semantic differential technique, and also eye-tracking technology, in order to check if differences were detected again, not only in subjective assessments, but also in objective parameters measured in participants' gaze behaviour.

Although the adjectives correlated with the ceramic flooring preference are in general those of symbolic meaning, it was decided to consider again also those with functional meaning, to avoid losing information. On the other side, the image of the empty room ("d") was removed, since it does not reproduce the same view of the room, and therefore it cannot be compared with the other three images.

Phase 2: application of semantic differential and eye-tracking techniques

In phase 2, an eye-tracking system was incorporated to the study to measure participant gaze over the ceramic flooring images. Thirty subjects participated (14 men and 16 women). Ten participants were assigned to each of the three furnished images used for the ceramic flooring assessment. The reason of using a small sample is due to recent studies that predict efficient outcomes with eye-tracking and other techniques combined (Fehd and Seiffert, 2008; Galotto and Ulloa, 2010; Liu, Lai and Chuang, 2011; Kwon and Sturt, 2014; Mitterer-Daltoé et al., 2014). The stimuli for the eye-tracking system were produced by combining each furnished room image (1200x900 pixels) with the semantic scales, as shown in Figure 3. Twelve stimuli were produced per image, one for each subjective impression in the questionnaire (see Table 1).

Procedure

Stimuli were displayed in a Tobii device (Tobii® TX300, www.tobii.com), with a 23" HD screen and the Tobii tracker located below the screen. The study was conducted in a room free from distractions, where

Figure 2. Confidence intervals (95%) for the mean. Assessment of "Innovative" (phase 1).

participants sat on a comfortable chair with the eye-tracking device system in front of them during a single session of no more than 10 minutes. The process is illustrated in Figure 4.

Initially, participants were given a personal questionnaire (so the research team could obtain demographic data), and listened to the test instructions. Next, they performed a gaze calibration guided by Tobii system followed by 20 second slide on the screen with the test instructions. After a five second delay, the study was launched. Each participant was randomly presented with the questions related to exactly one of the images shown in Figure 3. Stimuli were displayed on the screen for a limited amount of time based in similar studies (Jacob

Table 3. Correlations between preferences.

Correlation between "I like flooring/ I do not like it" and...	Spearman coefficient (p)
I like decorations/ I do not like them	0.463** (0.000)
Decorations adequacy: The furniture and the rest of decorative elements are suitable for the room flooring: Very appropriate/ Not suitable	0.228 (0.094)

Table 2. Spearman correlation coefficients between adjectives and flooring preference ("Like flooring").

Adjectives significantly correlated to "I like the flooring/ I do not like it" (Signification level < 0.05)	Spearman coefficient (p)	Adjectives not correlated to "I like the flooring/ I do not like it"	Spearman coefficient (p)
Natural/ Artificial	0.487** (0.000)	Expensive looking/ Cheap looking	0.168 (0.165)
Simple, versatile/ Excessively ornate, not adaptable	0.482** (0.000)	Brigth/Dark	0.144 (0.233)
Cosy/ Not cosy	0.416** (0.000)	Resistant/ Fragile	-0.103 (0.407)
Innovative / Traditional	0.414** (0.000)	Easy to clean/Difficult to clean	-0.002 (0.985)
Elegant/ Ordinary	0.404** (0.000)		

Figure 3. Stimulus (image and semantic scale) as shown to participants in our study. Images “a, b and c”.

Figure 4. Complete process scheme.

and Karn [2003] suggests a minimum of 100-200 milliseconds to obtain fixation data and verify sample rates of eye-tracking device).

The test was structured in two clusters: cluster A and B. The cluster A is comprised consecutively by the nine image/scale, the response time screen and the break screen. The stimuli “image/scale” were displayed for 3 to 5 seconds and the “response time” was displayed until the participants answered. The “break” screen displayed a white screen for 1 second. The cluster B is comprised consecutively by the three questions screen related to the decoration, the three image/scale, the response time screen and break screen. When the two clusters ended a screen informed about the end of test.

Data analysis

The eye-tracking system records various parameters from the observer, such as visual routes and heat maps, which can help identify relevant areas of the scene.

Visual routes are a representation of visual behavior, which exposes where the gaze of the subject was fixed at each moment, and the followed path. The visual routes for one participant and for all participants for

a given stimulus are shown in Figure 5.

Heat maps are a static representation of the analysis of visual patterns for a set of subjects. The heat maps for a participant and for all participants for a given stimulus are shown in Figure 5. To quantitatively analyze the ET results, we defined areas of interest (AOIs) for each image, differentiating between areas related to the ceramic flooring from areas containing decorative elements. The AOIs for each image are shown in Figure 6.

The time spent looking at different AOIs was extracted and the percentage of time spent looking at the flooring area was calculated (for each question, total seconds looking at the flooring area / total seconds looking at the stimulus, before answering). Reading time was not considered. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showed that variables cannot be considered to follow a normal distribution both for semantic differential data and percentage of time from eye-tracking.

As in the previous pilot phase, for the semantic differential data we have analyzed whether the judgment of the floorings (adjective assessments) are

Figure 5. In the left column: visual routes of a participant (top) and the 10 participants (bottom) that were assigned to image "a". In the right column: heat map of a participant (top) and of the 10 participants (bottom) to same image.

Figure 6. Areas of interest (AOIs) assigned to the images.

influenced by the type of decoration, to conclude that decoration styles can influence subjective impressions of the floorings. A Kruskal-Wallis test was applied to find out whether there were significant differences in the assessments, depending on the type of decoration (independent variable: type of decoration; dependent variables: assessment ratings to each pair of assertions -subjective impressions-). When the Kruskal-Wallis test showed significant differences, the Mann-Whitney U test for two independent samples was applied. Bonferroni adjustment was considered in order to control the probability of making type I errors. Since the 3 types of decoration need 3 pair comparisons (1-2, 1-3, 2-3), Bonferroni adjustment leads to a critical significance level for the decision of

$$p = 0.05/3 = 0.0166.$$

For the eye-tracking data, we have analyzed whether the judgment of the floorings (adjective assessments) are influenced by the time spent looking at the decoration areas, for each type of decoration. To check the possible influence of the types of decoration, the Spearman correlation coefficient between each rating assessment and the percentage of time looking at the decoration areas before answering (1 - the percentage of time looking at the flooring area) was calculated separately for each type of decoration. Additional application of the Kruskal-Wallis tests was performed to compare the assessments and gaze behavior, taking the type of decoration as the independent variable. The

Figure 7. Confidence intervals (95%) for the mean. Left: Assessment of "Innovative" (phase 2). Right: Percentage of time looking at decorations areas before assessing "Like flooring" (phase 2).

Mann-Whitney U test was also applied to compare women and men results (independent variable: gender).

Results

The Kruskal-Wallis test showed a significance value $p=0.034$ (<0.05) for "Innovative", so that significant differences in this assessment are found based on the type of decoration also in this second phase, although with a lower number of respondents. The subsequent application of the Mann-Whitney U test for two samples shows significant differences between images "a" and "b" ($p=0.035$) and between "b" and "c" ($p=0.029$), although significance values are higher than the adjusted critical significance level ($p=0.0166$). Figure 7 (left) shows the confidence intervals (95%) for the mean of "Innovative" assessment, for the 3 images.

In terms of the objective parameters obtained from eye-tracking, the Kruskal-Wallis test showed a significance value $p=0.038$ (<0.05) for the percentage of time looking at decoration AOIs before assessing "Like flooring", based on the type of decoration. The subsequent application of the Mann-Whitney U test for two samples shows significant difference between images "a" and "c" ($p=0.015$ <0.0166). This difference is shown in Figure 7 (right).

Besides, correlation coefficients between the assessment to each question and the percentage of time looking at the decoration AOIs before answering are only statistically significant between the percentage of time looking at decoration AOIs and the assessment of "Innovative" for image "a" (Figure 1) (Spearman coefficient: 0.636; $p=0.048$). That is to say, the more time spent looking at decorations, the more innovative the assessment for the ceramic flooring. This objective fact also seems to align with the idea that the decoration type influences the ceramic flooring perception.

Results of the semantic differential and eye-tracking analysis also reveal behavioral differences between men and women. Regarding to semantic differential analysis, the Mann-Whitney U test shows significant differences between women and men in the assessment of "Bright" and also in the assessment of "Like flooring" ($p=0.038$ and $p=0.043$ respectively).

Women seem to perceive the flooring brighter ($M_{\text{women}}=1.13$; $M_{\text{men}}=0.29$) and do not like the flooring while men do ($M_{\text{women}}=-0.56$; $M_{\text{men}}=0.5$).

Regarding eye-tracking data, significant differences have been also detected between women and men (Mann-Whitney U test) when answering the questions "Bright" and "Decorations adequacy". In particular, women spend a lower percentage of time looking at the decorative elements before answering to these questions than men do. The average percentage of time looking decorative areas before answering "Bright" are: $M_{\text{women}}=43.18\%$; $M_{\text{men}}=57.76\%$, and before answering about the decoration adequacy: $M_{\text{women}}=64.76\%$; $M_{\text{men}}=82.90\%$.

In addition, women make a higher percentage of visits to the ceramic flooring area than men do when answering "Decorations adequacy". The average percentages of times looking at the ceramic flooring are $M_{\text{women}}=36.53\%$, $M_{\text{men}}=17.12\%$. So, in the assessment of the context adequacy, women focus more on looking at the material, while men do in the decorative elements.

The results obtained are affected by the small sample size. The power of the analysis is limited, so that only very high differences have been detected as significant. That is to say, the probability of making type II errors in the analysis is very high; we have not probably found all the existing significant differences.

Conclusions

In this paper, we describe the results of a study designed to analyze the influence of different decoration styles on the subjective impressions evoked by a particular ceramic floor. The material is assessed through rendered images with different decorative elements. In the first phase, semantic differential technique was applied, whereas a combination of semantic differential and eye-tracking techniques was used in the second phase.

Results of the first phase showed that the decoration style used where a material is presented can influence certain subjective impressions related to the material. In our particular case, the rating assessment of the adjective "Innovative" for the ceramic flooring was

significantly different between two different decorations (images “a” and “b”).

The second phase of the study incorporated eye-tracking technique in order to check whether differences were detected again, not only in subjective assessments, but also in objective parameters measured in participants’ gaze behavior. Results showed a significant correlation between the percentage of time looking at the decoration areas for a particular decoration (image “a”) and the assessment for the adjective “Innovative”. This objective fact also seems to align with the idea that the decoration type influences the ceramic flooring perception. Due to the small sample size, the power of the analysis is limited. Consequently, we have probably made type II errors (we have not probably found existing significant differences). Eye-tracking techniques have also showed some differences in gaze behavior between women and men.

Based on the results of our study, we can conclude that the decoration style used where a material is presented can influence some subjective impressions evoked by the product in which that material is employed. The combination of the semantic differential with eye-tracking provide both subjective and objective measures of the impact of this contextual influence, giving a valuable information that can be taken into account to improve the design or customize it according to some specific group of users.

Finally, although the techniques used are based on different-natured data (subjective data, in the semantic differential technique, and objective data in ET), the results are related: in both cases a significant difference has been detected in the assessment of the image ‘a’ for the meaning ‘Innovative’. This result opens a new field of future work: to find the possible equivalence or complementarity of subjective and objective measurement techniques, in affective design.

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Banksy's Dismaland: A brief analysis of emotions through design

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Abstract This article does the relation between the approaches of emotion and Emotional Design with the artistic intervention called Dismaland, created by Banksy in association with other contemporary artists. In this art project there was a clear intention of stimulate people that enjoyed the park on emotions that make them think over social and cultural values. It's possible to relate Emotional Design with the established project, because there is a logic in demonstrate that emotion is a result of stimulus that people are lead to have about the contact with products and services, resulting on evaluations established on this context of information processes revealed on this experience. It's possible to recognize that, even leading to pleasant and unpleasant emotions, Dismaland fulfilled its intention on causing a reflection and social critic to current lifestyle and culture.

Keywords *Emotional design, Emotion, Design, Banksy, Dismaland*

Introduction

People are frequently boosted by stimulus that make them respond, in general, in an evaluative way, to the environment where they are inserted. This answer is related to interpretations that the brain makes and leads the body to respond in a physical way. As he develops the concept of emotion, Damasio (2000) resorts on respected authors like Willian James (1884) who, while analyzing the construct of other respected authors like Shakespeare, in the works *Otelo* and *Hamlet*, relates emotion to literary narratives and the way it can explore, besides the body, the cognitive sense of such concept. In this aspect, Damasio (2000, p. 74) defines:

Emotions are adaptations that integrate mechanisms which through the organisms regulate life, sometimes in a specific reaction to a situation, sometimes in the regulation of the inner state of the individual, whose job is to help the organism to preserve life.

It is necessary to address an assertion about emotion that, many times, causes misinterpretations. There is a difference between the concepts of emotion and feeling and other types of affective expressions. Emotion is defined through the understanding of the elements that compose the emotional state. (Scherer, 2005).

The elements that compose the emotional state are not related in a disconnected way, for this relation to happen, experience and stimulus make this interaction possible, which Damasio (1996) describes as "*not a luxury*", but a mental process of evaluation that is voluntary and not automatic:

The reactions to this broad spectrum of stimulus and situations can be filtered through a process of weighted deliberation. This reflexive and evaluative filter presents the possibility of variations on the

proportions and intensity of the pre-established emotion patterns and produces, as a result, a modulation in the basic machinery of emotions. (Damasio, 1996)

These emotional reactions create responses on the physical state of the individual that translates on pleasant and unpleasant sensations that many times can lead a person to keep away or approach the provocative stimulus, as Damasio (1996) comment:

If it didn't exist the possibility to feel the states of body, that are inherently destined to be painful or pleasant, there wouldn't be suffering or happiness, desire or mercy, tragedy or glory on human condition.

All the emotions triggered by experience suffer from the interference of the cultural context of each individual, and if the trigger is too strong, there is the possibility of lack of control on the responses. Paul Ekman (2003), pioneer psychologist on the study of emotions, says that there is a common base of emotional reactions, but the rest endures great influence of the cultural context and this affects the stimulus' interpretations. And the author also mentions that try to exercise control over these emotions won't always work, because when the raised emotion is too strong, the effort makes the interpretation difficult and forces the person to make precipitated decisions that can contribute in a negative way to the experience.

On these contributions, in the same way that Damasio used literature to analyze emotions, in this article, on a less extensive way, it's proposed, unpretentiously, to analyze the artistic intervention Dismaland of Robert Banks, mostly known by the pseudonym Banksy, English street artist. The research contextualizes from the meaning and types of emotions, looking for identify what emerges as it connects with this kind of

expression that comes from the art's world.

Dismaland is a park on Somerset, England, that was installed for a determined period, during August 22th to September 27th, 2015, under the intent to deconstruct the Disney magic and provoke a social critic.

To analyze the correlations between the emotional process, the approaches that come from the design for emotion and the artistic installation, it was chosen a qualitative method of research, anchored by bibliographic research and research on newspapers and periodicals about the subject, and the Dismaland work itself.

The method adopted was developed through a case study based on secondary data since it is an artistic intervention, without any academic bibliographic reference, the search for information was realized through websites, interviews and magazines. These informations were collected across a wide search on internet and selected considering some criterias as, for example, relevance of source. These represent a consistency to comment on the issue, including investigated within the site itself Dismaland, interviews in renowned magazines with the author, Banksy, and material published in journals coming from universities.

The research problem consists in the question: In which way the interaction with the Dismaland park can contribute to justified experiences through the Design for Emotion?

To take care of this problem it starts from a main objective, that it's to comprehend how the interaction with the Dismaland park can contribute to justified experiences through the Design for Emotion. Besides that, it delimitates specific objectives that are described below:

- a Analyze the approaches of the design for emotion;
- b Analyze the Dismaland park;
- c Relate the types of emotional approaches with the people's interactions with the Dismaland park.

To meet the goal "a" a literature was developed with the authors on the topic Emotional Design (section 2). To meet the goal "b" a survey was conducted through websites, magazines and periodicals that have addressed the subject studied, Dismaland, since there is no academic reference on this point (section 3). And to respond the objective "c", a content analysis based on the categories described in the theory was accomplished to see how they were manifested in the studied object (section 4).

This study is divided in understand the approaches of the Emotional Design, analysis of the Dismaland case from Banksy, discussion that relate the types of emotions and interactions emerged on Dismaland, and final considerations, as it's presented below.

The approaches of the Emotional Design

The user's experience with a designed product has as

Figure 1. Jordan's pleasures. Source: Adapted from Jordan (2000).

a result of this interaction an emotion that can be positive, negative or neutral. Besides this emotional aspects being themes of endless studies in Psychology, it was from de decade of 1990 that this subject became also a focus on Design studies. (Tonetto, 2013). The area that cares on investigate the emotions to help on the design of artifacts with the intention of avoid or provoke specific emotions is known as Emotional Design. (Demir et al, 2009). In this perspective, there are three most known approaches, developed by the authors Jordan (1999), Desmet (2002) and Norman (2004).

When the design starts to demand studies that direct the project further than its form and function, it starts to present intangible aspects that are strongly attached to the senses and emotions when linked by people during its interaction with the artifacts. Jordan (2000) is one of the authors that identified this interaction while analyzing the pleasure, which is an emotion, as a result of the use of a product. On that note, he listed four types of pleasures (Figure 1).

The physiological pleasure, that it's quite sensory, people can have it stimulated on the contact with the object through smell, touch, taste, sight or sound. The physiological pleasure can be represented, for example, when entering a cafeteria, and the smell of coffee being so delightful that make a person consume the product, for example. The experience is delightful, therefore to design keeping in mind the physiological pleasure, according to Jordan (2000), is important to ensure the consumption.

The other approach talks about social pleasure, this one related to status, social position. In this case, it's relevant to know the opinion of other people, of society, about what is consumed. Therefore design while contributing to stimulate this feeling of acceptance, of identity, should be considered on Jordan's (2000) point of view.

A third suggestion would refer to psychological pleasure, this one related to the cognitive. The interaction with the artifact is related to its usability.

Figure 2. Norman's levels. Source: Adapted from Norman, 2004.

The result of this relation, if positive, shows a high level of psychological pleasure, and the opposite can occur too. Negative experiences can be extremely nefarious, generating a lower level of pleasure, or even generating no pleasure at all. (Jordan, 2000).

At last, the author says that there's an ideological pleasure related to values and preferences that the human-object interactions generates. Questions arising from moral, culture, experiences, are present when this type of pleasure is stimulated. Another author that engaged on investigate emotions inside design's perspectives was Norman (2004), he assigned three levels of emotional processing: visceral, behavioral and reflective.

The visceral level is the most primitive contact that can be made with an artifact, intimately connected to the product's aesthetics. While interacting with an object, the human being reacts in a pleasant or unpleasant way, and this reaction comes from its first impression of this contact. The behavioral level is connected, on the other hand, to the product's function, the user's interactions will be judged from this perspective. At last, there is the reflective level, mostly related to the meaning that people attribute to products while interacting with them. It's a level mostly associated to culture, to the reflections that are made on the consumptions' process. (Norman, 2004).

The third approach that is presented here brings cognitive evaluations to understand the users' relations with emotions and is a result of Desmet studies (2002). The author utilizes the Appraisals' theory, which comes from psychology, initially on the sixties and more emphatically in the end of the eighties, from the studies of Fridja et al (1989) and adapts it to design. This theory discusses the relation of how emotions are a result of evaluations, which concentrate on a pattern (appraisal), all that reproduced by a stimulus that is related to the users' well-being. The stimulus will provoke a reaction on the person that, if it's positive, will be a pleased one and if it's a negative one, will result on displeasure.

Figure 3 presents the Model of Emotion with Product that Desmet (2002) developed to demonstrate that emotion comes from the evaluation of two elements,

Figure 3. Model of Emotion with Product. Source: Adapted from Desmet, 2002.

the *concern* and the product, being the first one the disposals that usually people bring to the emotional process. The evaluations (appraisals) are the result of this information process revealed on the interaction with the product, through the stimulus (concern). The Appraisal, according to psychology's vision, is an estimative or evaluation of the importance, sense and relevance of certain stimulus that are related to a person's well-being. Essentially, the appraisal of a situation causes an emotional or affective response, based on this evaluation (Frijda, 1986; Lazarus, 1991). This appraisal can be an automatic response for the following question: "What this situation means to my well-being?", if the answer is positive, the person will have a pleasant emotion, but if it's negative, the emotional resolution will be unpleasant. This ponderation helps the individual to recognize the greatness of the experienced situation in a way that an emotion emerges related as a reaction. In that way, each person (taking into account its social and cultural context) will offer a different estimative (or not) facing the same stimulus (Demir; Desmet; Hekkert, 2009).

The case: Banksy's Dismaland

Banksy is a pseudonym of a British graffiti artist, painter, political activist and movie director. His satirical and subversive street art combines black humor and graffiti made with a distinct stencil technique. His work of social and political comments can be found on streets, walls and bridges of cities all around the world. Banksy's work was born in the alternative scene of Bristol, and involved collaborations with other artists and musicians. Being known for his contempt for the government that considers graffiti as vandalism, Banksy exposes his art in public spaces like walls and streets, and even uses objects to show it (Figure 4). Banksy does not sell his work directly, but it's known that art auctioneers tried to sell some of his graffiti in the locals that they were made, letting the problem of how to remove the drawing in the hands of the buyers. (Manco, 2016).

Figure 4. Banksy's art. Source: banksy.co.uk.

Dismaland was an art installation based on *pop-up* books and represents a twisted Disneyland. The project was signed by Banksy, but the entire park has sculptures and interventions from 56 favorite contemporary artist of Banksy, besides presentations of some of the great names of the British music. (Edinboro, 2015). The park was built in a secret way on the city of Somerset in an abandoned resort, called Tropicana, on Weston-super-Mare, England. The name of the park is a pun with "dismal" and Disneyland (Figure 5). It was considered one of the biggest project of the artist so far and, as most of his work and performance, it was created on special secrecy. The residents of the English city thought that the construction of the huge Banksy's decoration was part of a Hollywood movie set. (G1.COM, 2016).

The artistic installations generate more than 20 thousand euros to the local economy, as in tourism companies, hotels and restaurants. The Dismaland ads said: "Are you looking for an alternative for the soulless sugar's coated banality for a day with family? Or just a cheaper place? So this is the place for you – a new chaotic world, where you can run away from the senseless escapism. Instead of a hamburger's tent, we have a museum. Instead of a gift store, we have a library. Well, we have a gift store too...". (Romanzoti, 2016).

Dismaland did a satirical critic to thematic parks. On what all the employees should be grumpy and with no desire to help the guests, the park circulation was thought so that huge lines were accumulated to see the attractions. The games and plays offered on the stands were very hard and barely unbeatable. There was no cleaning service, resulting on piles of garbage and forcing the visitors to detour from the dirt, contributing to the ambience of abandonment – and despair. Besides that, all park areas brought questioning to people about what is fun and the reflection about this experience. The abundance of crossing between modern industry sections, with museums looking for entertain and attractions looking for educate. Banksy took this to the extreme, creating an art gallery with a high level of emotional experience that is an amusement park. (Attractions,

Figure 5. Alternative poster of the park, with ground plan. Source: Google images.

2015).

Types of emotions and the interactions awoken on Dismaland

During the months that the artistic installation Dismaland was available, it provoked all kinds of reactions, as much by people who went to the park as through social media, where it was vastly referenced. Actually the artist and his project partners had in mind exactly that, bring a social critic that provokes discussion and great reflection about values and consumption nowadays. (Edinboro, 2015).

In this context it makes sense the need to explore all emotions that can be trigger while interacting with the park and its diverse proposal. When is established a relationship between Design for Emotion and its theories, it's clear that there is an intention on the project to cause exactly some emotions on the viewer. (Desmet, 2002). If the proposal is to make a social critic, why not stimulate the user to evaluate them, through this experience?

While analyzing the theories that come from the Emotional Design, its perceived on its different approaches, all of them propose to, through the analysis of the interaction between the emotions and some determined artifact, make possible that the designer take into consideration this relation during the project and helps to conceive a product that satisfies the consumer (Desmet, 2002; Jordan, 2000; Norman, 2004).

Under Jordan's perspective (1999, 2000), the physiological pleasure is represented on the contact

Figure 6. Dismaland. Source: Google images.

that people do with Dismaland, when visiting it there's a sensorial experience that register a stimulus to reflection, that could be pleasant or unpleasant, because there is an intention to shock on this visual interaction. The social pleasure is distinguished by questioning society, knowing what they think about what is really associated on the installations spread on the park. While the psychological pleasure is distinguished by generating a cognitive stimulus on who interacts with the proposal offered by Dismaland. The great reflection of Disney's antithesis, the magic and perfect world of fairytales.

Looking through Norman's optic (2004), it's possible to associate the park to visceral, behavioral and reflective emotional levels, which are stimulated on the interactions that were made during the contact with the artistic intervention. The visceral exposes the emotions related to the park's aesthetics, that many times can remind disorder, dirt and grotesque look, but the project planned precisely that, to shock the public. The behavioral level of this approach is intimately connected to the product's usability, on this aspect the utility of Dismaland is associated to causing commotion, stimulate emotions that perceive what is behind the work. And this question is also close to Norman's reflective level that suggests a project that instigates people to expand their emotions on this interaction. There is a latent meaning on Dismaland that emerges from the search to liquid consumerism, the life form that the XX century allowed itself and caused the sustainable current losses. Emotions about how to establish a social and cultural reflection are stimulated by this bias.

Yet the approaches investigated by Desmet (2002) can be assigned on the Dismaland project as the

interactions' exploration listed on Figure 3. The stimulus (concerns) caused by the contact with the product (park) generate evaluations that create emotions. In this case, the designers involved on the Dismaland project guaranteed an experience that had a critic, and even uncomfortable, unpleasant nature, on the user so that it would have a reflection about the role of society in the world. To provoke this stimulus would be necessary to generate questioning on people. The negative emotion in this sense was necessary to reach the project objective, related to its social critic.

And through the Appraisals' theory optic and through Ekman's vision (2003), Dismaland was the result of a very well planned project by Banksy, to provoke this negative emotions and with that generate questioning, but each person who went to the park received the same stimulus, but the deliberation about the emotional response takes into consideration the individual context of each guest. The perceptions of discomfort provoked in all park's spaces, helped on the affective negative responses (Fridja, 1986) as discomfort and even despair, as reported by some people that had the opportunity to experience the intervention. But also, other guests liked and remained for a long time on the park, participating on all offered events. They told that they felt pleasure with the negative emotions and that were comfortable with all the questioning that were stimulated. In this way, the cultural and social context of each person affected the evaluation of the experience with the park attractions.

Final considerations

This article proposed to bring a brief discussion about the theories that talk about emotion and the artistic intervention created by Banksy, the Dismaland park. In this analysis were referenced the users' interactions

with the park and what types of emotions could be awakened so it would generate a social critic of today's social values like consumerism and sustainability.

While being taken away to a different experience, the user was stimulated to reflect about the aspects related to culture nowadays. The interaction with Dismaland was the antithesis of the interactions that occur on the other amusement parks, because it generates some oddness and, in some cases, discomfort, because of works of high deconstruction impact similar to already existent works.

The theories that come from the Emotional Design relate emotional stimulus associated to the interactions that people are predisposed to do with products and services. According to one of these theories already referenced here, the Appraisals' theory project (Desmet, 2000), it's possible to awake emotions as much positives as negatives, during the project creation. Analyzing under this optic, Banksy and the artists invited to develop this installation, were responsible precisely to provoke negative emotions on the park guests so they would be lead to certain social questioning. In this sense, they were successful, because even who felt pleasure while enjoying all the possibilities that the park offered, was stimulated to wander through the park exactly because of emotions that would guarantee a more critic look on the work. Others, therefore, reported that the interaction with Dismaland provoked such displeasure that they preferred to leave the installation and not participate in all events.

If the intention was to shock, it was achieved. Banksy, on the other hand, affirmed on interviews that he could have been too gentle on the provocations established there, but during the project's elaboration, looking through the Emotional Design perspective, the emotions were stimulated intentionally. There is achievement on a project that can connect this emotional or affective stimulus through the evaluation that the users establish on their relations with the products-services (Fridja, 1986).

Therefore, it's considered that the Dismaland project was successful, because it stimulated people to question themselves about: "*What this situation means to my wellbeing?*". The answer could be as much positive as negative, generating delightful or not delightful emotional experiences, respectively. The important thing on this context was precisely to cause a commotion that would bring questioning about society and current lifestyle. (Demir; Desmet; Hekkert, 2009).

It became clear that the same stimulus can or cannot generate different perceptions in this experience, so it's important to address that different social and cultural contexts influence on these evaluations. But being good or bad, we can't disregard that this project turned people's experience in a memorable event.

Given the relevance of the object studied and the lack of academic research around the work, this is an initial study of the artistic intervention, Dismaland,

which encourages a future work from this one. The suggestion is that in a next step of this research, the study will not be based only on secondary data, it will contemplate an approach to end-users. It is believed that, doing this, will be able to conduct a deeply discussion the emotions aroused by the intervention.

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Emotions-based interactions: Design challenges for increasing well-being

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Abstract How to drive everyday life toward creativity and a positive state of mind? Can interaction design trigger emotions and reinforce well-being attitude? This paper is a first exploratory study of design research, trends and practices on how devices and interfaces could advance when engaging more deeply with the recognition of emotions. The purpose is to provide insights and resources across different perspectives for the understanding of the emerging landscape of emotion-based technologies and on how it can evolve with future interfaces involving well-being intent. The role of emotions in the design has been growing, this paper gathers the preliminary approaches to frame drivers that influence the design, especially dealing with new directions and visions to address well-being. Finally, it outlines some of challenges and future research opportunities.

Keywords *Interaction design, Positive emotions, Experience design, Emotional well-being, Future interfaces*

Introduction

In the pursuit of well-being this paper offers an exploratory study for framing the growing field of emotion-based technologies and describes futures research opportunities and challenges that might drive interaction design.

The vision that emotions can become input for the next future interactive systems and interfaces is fueled by the ongoing proliferation of sensor-based technologies that can recognize the peoples' emotional states. One of the key challenge in those system is the real-time tracking of emotions and the ability to relate them to behavioural data.

This open up a new territory with respect to the design of interactive interfaces able to drive pervasive sensitive systems in triggering positive emotions and, as core consequence, in improving well-being.

Why integrating positive emotions into the interaction design process?

Emotions are spontaneous and almost irrational reactions to external stimuli, in this manner they are naturally interactive overwhelming the human body which responds through various signals, physical and behavioural manifestations. Behavioural manifestations of emotions include various decision-making processes: consumption choices (Brandt, 2016), the perceived quality of social relationships (Reeves and Nass, 1996), effort and time used to interact with media and information technologies (Zhang, 2008) as well as about the state of mind habits.

Working with Positive Emotions, as fundamental component of the theory of well-being (Seligman, 2011) is the key to design meaningful experiences and to increase life satisfaction, because cognitive system

learns from experiences and provides an adaptive reaction.

The implications of enhancing personal well-being toward an upward spiral in increasing positive emotions (Friedrickson, 2002), are related to several aspects that affect human psychology such as motivation, self-esteem, creativity, competence, trust, achievement, gratification and so on. Trigger positive emotions is a practical method that can help to release endemic disorders of the information society such as stress, anxiety and depression. Moreover, experiencing positive emotions can optimize psychological resilience and increase health benefits and even longevity (Ekman, 2003). These findings indicate a reciprocal connection among design research, psychology, social science and behavioural change perspective that outlines the great complexity of defining new tool and methodologies (Sanders, 1999) to design interfaces that facilitate positive people's life experiences.

While much of technological advancement within emotion recognition borrowed its theoretical framework from cognitive psychology to analyse and drive emotions conveyed by products, the social sciences within interactive systems were slower to suggest new applications. This common ground could help designer and researchers to access the emotional experience in a way that would improve well-being.

How to building the emotional connection between people and new form of interfaces is part of the design research advancement (Yagou, 2006). In this framework this research aims to outlines possible directions to address the interaction design for emotional well-being.

Background and related work

The psychologist Paul Ekman (2003) argues that there are two steps to improve our emotional life. One is to be aware of emotions, learn to read them and recognize their expression, the second step is to realize when we are responding emotionally, reactions and situations. This awareness can increase the gap between impulse and action to stimulus. In the same way interaction design processes can follow this path activating emotional experiences and self-awareness through new solutions.

We could be inspired by the term 'positive' as a way to focus on the mechanism to encourage cognition and action toward meaningful individual improvements, building optimism, for instance, increase self-esteem, energize goal-achievement.

Positive psychology movement has grown quickly in the last 15 years. It is the scientific understanding of the conditions and processes that contribute to the flourishing or optimal functioning of people, groups and institutions (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000, Reeve, 2014).

According to Fredrickson's broaden-and-build theory (2001), positive emotions - including amusement, interest, joy, contentment, pride in achievement, love, interest, satisfaction, sensory pleasure - encourage people's exploration thought actions. Play for instance, is an activity that helps balancing physical, intellectual and social skills that fuels creative thinking development and the ability of learning (Callois, 1958). Phenomenologically all positive emotions share the ability to build people's personal resources and culture by creating the urge to explore, taking in new experiences and expanding the self in the process. Although positive emotions can be valued as subjective experiences that occur in specific circumstances, they move individuals toward a better mindset developing cognitive skills essential to well-being. Courage, happiness, motivation, engagement, self-esteem, hope as well as wisdom, forgiveness are all individual traits that trigger our own emotional responses that turn colors to our interpretation of actions, situations and relationships (Ekman, 2002).

More recently, Martin Seligman (2011) provides the PERMA conceptual model of well-being that consists in five elements: (1) positive emotions, (2) engagement, (3) positive relationships with others, (4) meaning and purpose to belong a part of something bigger than themselves, and (5) accomplishment that is the sense of achievement. Those five measurable elements could help individuals find paths to flourishing.

However life satisfaction has different life status variables, called 'circumstances' (cultural, political and economical situations) that influence peoples' well-being (Seligman 2016; Helliwell, 2016). In recent years, the engagement nature of interactive technologies has offered new possibilities in the area of intentional activities (Lyubomirsky, 2006) that are actions and practices that people choose to engage and invest effort to enact.

Emotions, from amusement to awe, interest, gratitude, curiosity and fear, are studied and applied in combination to other media, entertainment, interactive products and game design. XEODesign conducted several research studies on how computers and video games trigger emotions. Using facial expression analysis Nicole Lazzaro and team (2004) measured player's emotional responses identifying over thirty emotions. The experiences the game creates provide enjoyment, engagement, motivation, fun and altered state. The observation of facial gestures, body language and verbal comments revealed also excitement, frustration amusement as well as sensory pleasure derived from a rich experience of digital playing. Playing with games, we can experience the three kinds of positive emotions highlighted by Seligman (2011): (1) pleasure and gratification, (2) embodiment of strengths and virtues and (3) meaning and purpose. Interestingly, these same powerful traits create the contexts through which people are motivated in pursuing their goals, training their skills and in making their choices within an activity context (Weiser et al. 2015). Face and body expressions are crucial to the development of future interactive interfaces for well-being because they are not only display of emotions but generates beliefs and contribute to improve successful engagement and purpose.

Emotions and interactions

At their juncture, emotions and interaction design can play a very important role in improving the quality of life. Some studies on game design field suggest that emotions can be an important resource that interaction design cannot ignore as they move people to be proactive (McGonigal, 2011).

To date, design has engaged with emotions that show some cognitive characteristics of those involved on how people frame their relationship with objects, devices and others. Norman (2004) defines this emotional interaction with objects as visceral, behavioral and/or reflective. Those three correspondent design levels reveal also the personality of a product mediating behaviours across space and networks. Thus, consumers are led to choose their own interactive services and objects based on those experience. Gaver (1999) argues that emotion is a subset of the irrational in the design of technologies. Every artifact conveys emotions from users since the interaction with them implies spontaneity, intuition and elicit cultural connotations. However, rather than pursuing a computational approach to emotions, Gaver (2009) has also discussed a broader view of interaction design in which emotional experiences become the outcomes of people's engagement. In fact, enjoyment, motivation and sense of achievement are among the most desired experiences in interacting with digital games and playful artifacts. Furthermore autonomy, competence and relatedness are also innate psychological needs which lead to spontaneous players' emotional investment (Deterding, 2015).

These reciprocal relations among positive emotions, design and well-being need a wider systemic perspective. Hence, the influence of emotions on the

design of interfaces is not restricted to one source of experience - leisure, communication, marketing - but also it might be of interest exploring multiple sources for instance self-consciousness circumstances, or contexts to encourage behavioral change or to suggest sustainable living practices. For example design can drive positive emotional responses derived by the interaction with a system of connected objects ables to stimulate conversation, creativity and personal growth.

Many smart applications are already on this path pursuing several objective: training for self-awareness and healthy nutrition (Jiyo), meditation (Headspace), positive attitude (Uplifted), positive relationship (Couple), stress management (Empatica).

Design provides interconnectivity that is the potential of recent HCI and sustainability related research. Prototypes are starting to embed emotions in a variety of new sensing technologies often associated with the Internet of Things (IoT) vision (Koreshoff et. al, 2013), pervasive, ubiquitous and affective computing. Equipped with sensing technologies, interconnected interfaces can finely track behaviors and contexts promoting well-being and collective awareness through sharing and behavior change support (Castri, 2014).

This rapidly growing of pervasive sensing technologies can move interaction design to extend the benefits of emotional engagement in the direction of well-being.

Table 1 shows a summary of the relevant emotions-related research efforts mentioned. The various domains, focus and influences could be extended to new domains from arts to humanity covering new areas such as public, urban environments and domestic contexts which may address the interplay of techniques in developing interfaces able to interact with people's emotions and possible desires.

Emotions-based interfaces

In humans, emotions entail distinctive, integrated, and intimate ways of interacting, they impact on individual's everyday experiences, decision making, feelings, interpersonal relationships and behaviors. The understanding of what emotional triggers are, is

the core also of advertising effectiveness and media environment design and distribution. However there is a wide research area in developing technologies ables to handle data related to emotions. Face is the preeminent medium of emotional expression detection, but also speech patterns, body gestures and physiological reaction to stimuli are starting to be tracked and analyzed by computing systems.

On one hand, the accuracy of sensors and tracking systems are becoming sharper and intelligent. Cameras and microphones can detect facial or voices expressions and infer emotional state to a system database. It is the case of the commercial product Emotient (2016), an automatic and real-time detection system for objects analysis, in particular faces and muscles movements and attitudes prediction. This technology detects and measures mood, stress, sentiments, gender and age witnessing for the first time an expansion of emotion analytics capabilities in different sectors including automotive, medical technology and market research.

On the other hand affective computer systems are seeking to identify human emotional states and correlating physiological responses. Beyond detection of such changes in skin temperature, perspiration, heartbeat or nervous system signals, these bio-modules are often embedded in wearable devices - such as Affectiva measurement technology (Swinton, 2012) - enabling the emotional impact analysis. As a consequence, emotional data retrieved could act as input to change interfaces behaviors in response to user's emotional expression and trigger an incremental process.

Although some new relationships between technologies and emotions are still evolving, they can have implications in design and functions allowed.

The fast moving consumer goods industry connected to emotions measurements technologies shows a growing interest to understand how emotions affect our decisions making process to buy, be motivated and interact (Brandt, 2016). The early real-time prototype of Fraunhofer (2012), for instance, enables the detection of four families of emotions that are happiness, anger, sadness and surprise. Their technology has been already combined in Google Glass

Table 1. Research areas involved in emotions and design.

Domain	Area of focus	Influences
Positive Psychology	Positive emotions, meaning, happiness and flow, psychological resilience	Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi (2000), Fredrickson (2001, 2002), Reeve (2014), Lyubomirsky (2005)
Affective computing	Bi-directional communication, Bio-metrics, sensing	Picard (2001), Kanjo, Al-Husain and Chamberlain (2015)
Design and Entertainment	Disruptive purposive, play, product interaction design and ambiguity	Lazzaro (2004), Fogg (2009), Gaver (2009), McGonigal (2011), Deterding (2015)
Neuroscience	Conscious and non-conscious user responses, emotions measurement and motivation, emotional design	Ekman (2003), Norman (2004)
IoT and ICT	Haptic interactions, connections of interfaces, networks,	Koreshoff (2011), Zhang (2008)

demonstrating how wearable devices can be used to distinguish different types of emotional expressions in natural settings. What foreground this phenomenon of pervasive sensing technologies is the issue of quantitative measure the emotional experiences of individuals.

Further, quantitative data is going to be related to user behaviour analyzing context and conditions in which experiences affect emotional well-being. For example, Neumitra (2016) application links the user's stress level to their social mediated activities giving personalized feedback.

Early in 2002, the call for a design change went out, and the Affective Computing Research Group (Picard, 2002) has argued that human-computer interaction is social and emotional and as technology is changing, more designers can consider new points of views integrating interfaces to facilitate emotional and social communication. Now, the Affective Computing field embraces the approach that human-computer interaction should recognize and responds to user's emotions in a way that helps users meet their needs with emotionally supportive interactions (Picard, 2001).

Proceeding from this point, the design of technologies can extend these theoretical findings to produce significant results. What if self-esteem, happiness, motivation, engagement reactions become important keys to address the development of next future interfaces systems? Key to connect these approaches is the integration of positive emotion research in programming interfaces. Together with verbal, facial or gestures recognition tools interaction design is a reliable way to move the emotion analytics toward something that can generate important personal data resources for promoting well-being and supporting positive experiences. While commercial products are going to cover a broader range of domains, we can imagine future systems that can learn from humans' emotions encouraging people making better choices for their life. The reciprocal relation among design and emotions affecting each other will shape next future behaviors.

Designing for emotional well-being

Although there is still no comprehensive definition for emotional-based interfaces, emotions emerge in the design process as a real quality of the intentional interactions between humans and interfaces.

Emotions are important motivational triggers that energize and direct behaviors (Zhang, 2008; Fogg 2009). Working with those motivational lens is also an important and powerful source in providing guidance to ICT design as tools for understanding factors that lead a behavior shift into happiness and well-being attitudes.

Positive intentions cannot exist just at an abstract level. Here we approach the definition of the emotional drivers by mapping the core features into a circular structure (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Mapping emotional drivers and factors contributing to well-being.

The approaches reviewed in this study show a broad canvas of emotions. The revealed emotions are associated with six factors that influence well-being in the daily life: optimism, creative thinking, resilience, positive relationship, self-esteem and engagement.

The map is an insight guidance for HCI designers. That is, increasing their effort in exploring users' emotions through playful interfaces, designers should understand how to interact through them with a certain amount of flexibility - and invisibility - and better fulfill moods, attitudes and individual preferences.

Good responsible design shows a clear expansion of the technology advancement and a transformation of processes for a sustainable change.

Accordingly to the primary question addressed in this article: through what challenges can design include emotions to increase the well-being level, some movements can be defined across a number of disciplinary dimensions. Those provide clues into some of the factors that predicts future developments.

- *Sensing devices: environmental or wearable interfaces, either unobtrusive, pervasive and invisible. A more deep integration of cognitive and emotional data resources into systems able to read emotional processes and understand their circumstances.*
- *Models of well-being: development of open-ended sensing prototypes to observe patterns of positive behaviours and train people response-ability skills. This design-driven approach supports the analysis of emotional feelings related to daily life experiences.*
- *Adaptative tools: a broader combination of techniques and methodologies to read variance in emotions and be able to reply in a meaningful way. These allow people to elicit their emotions*

and to increase their self-awareness process for an emotional well-being enhancement.

- *Networked experiences: take into account the opportunity people have to share their emotions. This means considering links among biometric data, interaction environments and daily life behaviours. And more bridge those data at social level through networked media.*

Nowadays, the tendency is to prototype applications to train self-awareness, next step is to combine these with automatic emotional sensing technologies to promote adaptive contexts based on personal data resources. A step further is to design broader thought-action social environments direct to support individual growth and social transformation.

While various techniques and tracking tools are growing toward improving quantitative measurement, new systems are starting to connect emotional data with users habits at both individual and social layers. IoT prototypes and new wearable connected devices could be a support accompanying a sustainable change in mediating well-being.

Conclusions

This research aims at overcoming the design approach to draw emotional motivation towards products, goods and services, suggesting interaction design to include emotions-based technologies as part of the next future interfaces ecosystem.

The model encompass a wide variety of findings and suggests a number of new directions. Investigating emotional-based interaction various design approaches and research communities become engaged together encouraging well-being perspective. Advances in sensing technologies development, user experience and positive psychology have opened up practical ways to further include emotion-related human aspects into the design process.

In this landscape design and in particular interaction design, has the opportunity to support people's proactive experiences, enhance emotional well-being and, as consequence, improve the quality of life. Incorporating emotions into the design work means to add another level into the practice and then considering three aspects of the project: one is the technology to read, interpret and adapt to humans' emotions, the second is the behavioural level and what is connected to people's activities, believe system, daily life and experiences to use products and interfaces and the third is the emotional level and what moves people to act, to growth and to connect each other through different languages and media. It is finally time for the issue of emotional interaction design to be given the attention that it deserve for developing next future environments and interfaces towards well-being.

The question of how to create the relations between emotional well-being and design, as manifested in this research, embraces a long-term vision of integrating different perspectives and needs further expansion. We come together with Design and Emotion

community to present this exploration and invite a dialog regarding next future progresses.

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Where do people feel emotions in their body? A quantitative implementation of the Emotionally}Vague project

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Abstract The present paper presents the results of a collaborative project between an artist and two scientists interested in the embodiment of emotion. In the qualitative Emotionally}Vague project participants were asked to draw on a body outline where or how they felt anger, joy, fear, sadness and love. Inspired by the results of the Emotionally}Vague project, a quantitative study was performed to further examine people's body-emotion associations. For twenty-one emotions participants could choose a location and a possible second location on a body outline to indicate where they felt that emotion. The results demonstrated that emotions differed in where in the body they were felt. Notably, pride, anger, contempt and curiosity were associated with higher positions in the body as compared to pleasure, fear, guilt and disgust. Furthermore, as expected, there was individual variation in body-emotion associations. For all emotions, there was a sub-set of people that reported a body-emotion association not mentioned by another subset of people. These results support a view that emphasizes individual variability in the embodiment of emotional experience. Both scientific and practical applications of the task used to collect this data are discussed.

Keywords Emotion, Bodily states, Embodiment, Visual design

Introduction

Emotions are embodied. When people experience emotions, changes may occur in the activation of the autonomic nervous system, hormones may be released and facial or bodily muscles may contract (see for an overview Mauss & Robinson, 2009). These bodily sensations become part of people's personal beliefs or concepts about what emotions are and how emotions affect people (see Oosterwijk & Barrett, 2014; Oosterwijk, Mackey, Wilson-Mendenhall, Winkielman, & Paulus, 2015).

Even though the link between emotions and the body is well-established (Barrett, 2012; Damasio, 1999; Craig, 2008), it is debated whether the representation of emotions in the body is stable across people (i.e., the universal or "basic" emotion view; see Ekman, 1992; Nummenmaa, Glerean, Hari, & Hietanen, 2014) or whether there is meaningful variation in how people represent emotions in their body (i.e., a constructionist view of emotion; see Barrett, 2009; 2012). One way to test these opposing ideas is to map where people feel emotions in their body and to examine differences and commonalities.

The present paper describes a collaboration between a visual designer and two emotion scientists interested in the embodiment of emotion. The visual designer developed a survey method to explore in a qualitative fashion where people felt emotions in their body. This survey method was subsequently implemented in a quantitative study to test differences and

commonalities in where people felt emotions in their body. The present paper presents these results to forward new insights into the individual differences of body-emotion associations, but also to show, as a proof of principle, that experimental design projects can be applied in a scientific context.

The Emotionally}Vague project

In the project Emotionally}Vague (O'Brien, 2007; <http://www.emotionallyvague.com>) the focus was to qualitatively explore the question: "Do people feel emotions in their bodies?". The project involved the development of an original method in which participants were asked to draw on a paper body outline where or how they felt anger, joy, fear, sadness and love. The test phase included texture use, value, space selection, and alternative media such as stickers. The final survey had three variations of body map questions: fully open, "one spot only" and arrows to indicate direction. A sample of 250 people was gathered which included 38 nationalities with ages ranging from 6 to 75 years old.

To aggregate the results, each drawing was scanned. Then, the body outline was stripped away and all drawings were layered in Adobe Photoshop. The opacities were reduced to 15% in order to allow for the 'onion-skin' effect. This allowed for the highest and lowest densities of aggregated locations to be revealed. Figure 1, 2 and 3 demonstrate the results for the fully open questions, "one-spot only" questions and the directional questions, respectively. For the

Anger Joy Fear Sadness Love

Figure 1. Original representation of the results from the EmotionallyVague project (Fully-open responses).

Anger Joy Fear Sadness Love

Figure 2. Original representation of the results from the EmotionallyVague project ("One spot only" responses).

Anger Joy Fear Sadness Love

Figure 3. Original representation of the results from the EmotionallyVague project (Directional responses).

Figure 4. Overview of first locations for each discrete emotion category.

one-spot only questions undeniable patterns were revealed, despite many participants adding many more spots. The directional question revealed how the experience of emotion was one of a shifting pattern where movement was integral to the experience. Anger was represented mainly in head and chest and moved outwards from the head; joy emanated from the chest and filled the whole body; fear moved inwards to the abdomen; sadness had a downward direction and love was an all-body experience moving outward.

A quantitative implementation of the EmotionallyVague project

In an online study, the body outline from the EmotionallyVague project was used to explore body-emotion associations for twenty-one emotions often studied in emotion and affective science.

Method

Participants

One-hundred-and-sixty subjects (92 females; Mean age = 31.5 years) participated in an online study called "Drawing Emotion" for a small financial reward. The study was approved by the relevant Institutional Review Board, and all participants gave informed consent prior to starting the study.

Task

The task was presented on the website Mechanical Turk and programmed as an online questionnaire

using Qualtrics. Participants were presented with twenty-one emotions each combined with the outline of a body. For the full set of emotions, please see Figure 4. For each emotion participants were asked to choose one location that represented where they felt that emotion the most. When the participants clicked on the body outline a pointer appeared that could be moved around to find the location that best represented where they felt an emotion (first reported y -coordinate). The location was saved as an x -coordinate and a y -coordinate. After they entered the location where they felt the emotion the most, they could enter another location on the body outline (alternative y -coordinate). It was emphasised that there were no right or wrong answers. After finishing the body task, the participants filled in three questionnaires that will not be discussed further in this paper. Finally, participants were asked for their gender, age and ethnic background.

Analyses

We analysed differences between the first reported y -coordinate for the twenty-one emotion categories with a repeated measures ANOVA. Because many participants did not report a second location, this analysis was not performed for the alternative y -coordinate. An analysis of the x -coordinate did not demonstrate consistent results and is not discussed in this paper. To examine individual differences, each first reported y -coordinate and alternative y -coordinate was categorised as belonging to the head,

chest or belly (and lower) area of the body. Based on these variables we categorised the y -coordinate(s) for each emotion as felt only in the head, chest or body (i.e., no alternative y -coordinate was given) or as felt in the head-chest, head-belly or chest-belly. We also created a variable that reported the total number of emotions felt only in the head, chest and belly, or in the head-chest; head-belly and chest-belly.

Results

An analysis of the main y -coordinate demonstrated that emotions were associated with relative different positions in the body along the y -axis, $F(20, 3040) = 17.63, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .10, \epsilon = .73$. In particular, pride, anger, contempt and curiosity were associated with higher positions in the body (i.e., more towards the head), whereas pleasure, fear, guilt and disgust were associated with lower positions in the body (i.e., more towards the belly). See Table 1 for an overview of all paired comparisons. In general, positive emotions were felt more often in the chest than negative emotions, $t(157) = 9.29; p < .0001$, whereas negative emotions were felt more often in the head, $t(157) = -3.29; p < .001$, and belly, $t(157) = -5.99; p < .0001$, than positive emotions.

On average, participants filled in an alternative y -coordinate for 13.7 out of 21 emotions. This alternative location was combined with the first reported location to map individual differences in body-emotion associations. Figure 5 clearly demonstrates that participants vary in their associations between emotion categories and locations

in the body. For all emotions, there is a sub-set of people that reports a body-emotion association that is not mentioned by another subset of people. For example, some participants felt disgust, disappointment and embarrassment only in the head (22%, 19% and 30% respectively); whereas other participants felt these same emotions only in the belly (27%, 16% and 17% respectively). Even though many emotions demonstrated variety in body-emotion associations, other emotions were relatively strongly associated with particular areas of the body. For example, 75% or more of the participants mentioned only the chest, or a head-chest or belly-chest combination for joy, happiness, love and pride.

In terms of demographics, the results demonstrated that adults younger than 40 reported a lower mean y -coordinate across all emotions as compared to adults of 40 years and older, $F(1, 151) = 6.41, p < .05, \eta^2_p = .04 (M = 117.23 \text{ vs. } M = 102.56)$. Furthermore, younger adults felt a larger number of emotions only in their belly than older adults, $F(1, 158) = 9.51, p < .01$. We found no effect of the gender of participants when analysing the first reported y -coordinate. Nevertheless, when analysing the combined variables, we found that males felt a larger number of emotions only in their head, $F(1, 158) = 4.28, p < .05$, whereas females felt a larger number of emotions in the chest-belly region, $F(1, 158) = 4.05, p < .05$.

Discussion

The present paper presents the results of a collaborative project between an artist and two

Table 1. Comparisons between averaged y -coordinate for each emotion category.

	Mean Y	pl	fe	gu	di	Re	ex	lo	di	sh	pi	sa	je	jo	ha	em	ha	su	pr	an	co	cu	
pleasure	161																						
fear	145																						
guilt	145																						
disgust	138																						
relaxation	138																						
excitement	131																						
love	128																						
disappoint.	128																						
shame	113																						
pity	113																						
sadness	111																						
jealousy	106																						
joy	104																						
hate	102																						
embarras.	102																						
happiness	102																						
surprise	101																						
pride	93																						
anger	92																						
contempt	91																						
curiosity	53																						

Note: The first column reports the averaged first reported y -coordinate for each emotion category. The coloured columns represent Bonferroni corrected pairwise comparisons between emotion categories. Yellow cells represent $p < .05$; orange cells represent $p < .01$; red cells represent $p < .001$. Grey cells indicate that the mean y -coordinate did not differ between emotion categories.

Figure 5. Overview of combined first reported and alternative y-coordinate, categorised into head, chest and belly area.

scientists interested in the embodiment of emotion. The qualitative EmotionallyVague project forwarded interesting visual displays of where people felt anger, joy, fear, sadness and love in their body. This inspired a quantitative, online study into people's body-emotion associations. The findings of this study extend work by Nummenmaa and colleagues (2014) that used a similar method. In those studies the prime aim was to examine aggregated data, whereas the present quantitative study zoomed in on individual variation. Although the present data forwards similar aggregated patterns in the body across emotion categories as Nummenmaa and colleagues, the present data also supports the idea of individual variation in body-emotion associations. Indeed, our analyses show that different people felt the same emotion in different parts of their body (e.g., some people felt disgust, disappointment or embarrassment only in the head whereas others felt these emotions only in the belly). In addition, the present data expands the current knowledge on body-emotions associations by adding a set of emotions that have not been studied before (i.e., pleasure, relaxation, excitement, joy, curiosity, disappointment, embarrassment, pity, jealousy, hate, and guilt).

The results from the present project have several scientific implications. First of all, the present data demonstrates not only that *emotions* differ in where in the body they are felt, but also that *people* differ in where in their body they feel emotions. This latter finding is consistent with views that emphasise individual variability in emotional experience (Barrett, 2009), embodiment (Oosterwijk & Barrett, 2014) and sensitivity to bodily signals (Herbert & Pollatos, 2012). The present data also sheds some new light on the relationship between body-emotion associations and demographics. For example, the finding that older adults associate emotions to a lesser extent with the lower parts of their body, is consistent with the

suggestion that older adults lose sensitivity for the physiological condition of their body (Mendes, 2010).

In terms of future research, it would be relevant to explore whether the body task can indicate *trait* differences (i.e., stable individual differences in associations between emotions and the body) and *state* differences (i.e., situationally dependent variation in associations between emotions and the body) in body-emotion associations. Moreover, future research should examine to what extent the associations that people report reflect measurable physiological sensations, outward bodily expressions or symbolic/metaphoric associations (Kövecses, 2003). In addition, it is an open question what people represent when they choose a location in the head. Do these locations represent a sensation (i.e., a feeling in the throat, see disgust), a behaviour (i.e., smiling, see joy and happiness) or a cognitive representation of an emotion (i.e., angry thoughts, or a mental state of curiosity)? A qualitative approach that asks people explicitly what they portray when choosing a body location may shed more light on these questions.

The results from the present project also have important practical applications. For example, the body task could be used to map people's bodily sensations in a medical setting. It could facilitate non-verbal or distance dialogue between patient and therapist/doctor or as an alternative evaluative module in questionnaires such as for stroke rehabilitation or chronic pain. It could also be a tool for mindfulness and self-monitoring (e.g., a visual mood diary). Furthermore, it may have applications in commercial qualitative market research, as well as a tool for improving HR feedback and engagement. And finally, there are exciting possibilities for the collection of real-time, global responses through a future digital web version, leading to data visualisations on a mass scale. These visualisations

may be interesting as an art piece created by audience inputs, for example as an interactive component of theater, dance or music performances.

In closing, the findings from the present project have potential scientific and practical use. With this, the present project illustrates the importance of interdisciplinary collaborations between psychology and the field of arts and design and demonstrates that such collaborations can be both inspiring and fruitful.

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HOSPITABLE: Domestication of healthcare

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Abstract The hospital is the traditional and familiar controlled environment where healthcare is defined and delivered. However the consequences of an older society the escalating costs of healthcare services and a shortage of personnel and facilities have put pressure on the healthcare system to deliver more support and treatments on an outpatient basis and in peoples home. The home and the hospital bring together very different cultural practices and environments and this inexorable geographical shift in care has potential impact on our physical and emotional relationship with our home space – our domain. These cultural practices/experiences can be mediated through objects, which in turn can provide vehicles through which to gain understanding of the richness and complexity of people's lives. The authors draw on the value of 'thinking with things' as a methodology. Central to this approach is the notion of 'exhibition' as a research tool that becomes a meeting space that enables this methodology to be applied. The 'exhibition' provides a theatre for conversation and offers the medium and method for discourse, data collection creating the conduit, through which societal assumptions relating to ageing and healthcare care can be made visible, explored and challenged.

Keywords *Design, Healthcare, Critical artefacts, Aesthetics, Exhibition as research*

Introduction

The challenges society faces in providing future healthcare suggests radical changes to the way health services are delivered and the way we engage with them. There is recognition that this is likely to demand more self-management and a shift of care from the hospital to our home. Home has different meanings for people but it is generally agreed to be a place of comfort, security and emotional well-being. It is a private place that reflects our identity with who we choose to share. It is where we live and where most people would prefer to die.

'Italy: The New Domestic Landscape' an exhibition at MOMA (Museum of Modern Art, New York) in 1972 was a seminal moment in Design history. A series of prototype environments and installations by leading Italian designers would reflect upon changing domestic living patterns within contemporary society. This hypothetical existence included "permanent nomadism," "life without objects," and "life without work. The exhibition is generally regarded as a statement that design in Italy was moving beyond being an applied art and was becoming a language capable of making a commentary on reality. While we have witnessed much of the prophecy of the exhibition of 1972, the domestic landscape is once again the site of radical change impacted by the inevitable changes in the environmental and contextual shift of our healthcare services. This paper describes a methodological approach employed by the authors that explores the role of critical artefacts and their use as physical metaphors to prompt discussion that may help inform our understanding and emotional relationship with this new hybrid ambiguous

landscape. We will briefly discuss how future care at home might challenge the symbolic meaning and relationships within our home and its object infrastructure.

Context

Foucault (Foucault 1963) described the 'medical gaze' where the hospitalised individual becomes a patient, then an object, through the practices of medicine. Foucault argues that the hospital was organised as an 'examining apparatus' enabling almost constant observation of the patient. In this creation all extraneous variables such as the home environment, family, friends and usual activities were excluded, the hospital providing the ideal laboratory setting where the causes of symptoms could be isolated and the effects of treatment monitored. Gardner (Gardner 2000) warns the ambience and safety of the home can potentially be shattered by the invasion of illness-related technology. The invasion of the technology of acute care into the home has the potential to destroy the nurturing and therapeutic environment of home as a means of promoting health recovery. He states while care of the sick in their homes invariably and increasingly brings with it technology, this technology needs to fit into the home environment without dominating it and transferring the anti-therapeutic culture of the hospital environment into the home. He advocates a need to develop sensitivity to the space of the home as one of sanctuary with multiple social and emotional functions that serve to increase the well-being of people in health and illness.

Milligan in her book, *'There's no place like home: Place and Care in an Ageing Society'* (Milligan 2009),

Figure 1. 'Future bathroom'. Older people engaging with 'things' related to bathroom activities to develop understanding of use.

describes the significance of the home as a social space and points to why healthcare providers may encounter resistance from people and their families in their attempt to reorganise domestic settings to accommodate the healthcare needs of the care recipients and to satisfy health and safety requirements (Phillipson 2007). She suggests that the desire to improvise or subvert the logics of care aids in order to retain a sense of home and ownership produces an ambiguity of place both for carer and care-recipient - one that brings home and care into tension as the aesthetics of health care systems jostle against the aesthetics of home. So while professional care support within the home may be beneficial to the informal carer and care recipient, they also transgress the social space of the home often creating change in the symbolic meaning of home.

The 'smart' house

The invisible nature of digital infrastructures into our homes in some way realises the vision of the New Domestic Landscape that presented a hypothetical life without objects. McGuirk (McGuirk 2015) discusses how the internet-of-things evangelists proclaim that it is the most 'disruptive' of phenomena and suggests 'the network is the new electricity' which itself was arguably one of the greatest environmental revolutions. This digital network provides real opportunity to deliver healthcare at home integrated into the new domestic landscape now often defined as the Smart house. The smart home is now becoming a reality with 84% of homes in the UK connected to the internet, an increase from 59% in 2006 (gov.uk) however the smart house is not the abstract aesthetic of 1972 but manifested within existing dated and diverse housing stock. England has one of the oldest dwelling stocks in Europe with 21% of dwellings built before 1919 and 16% built between 1919 and 1945. Much of the existing 26 million houses in the UK is expected to be standing in 2050 (gov.uk). The connected house, according to McGuirk, with a proliferation of smart, connected products that will turn the home into a prime data collection node, 'is becoming a data factory'. This data will be transmitted and stored by the manufacturers of these products and we will witness the erosion of privacy. This 'surveillance' might for example lead to patterns of

control, facilitate 'nudge' tactics to change our behavior and provide access to our state of health that may have implications on our personal insurance. Rem Koolhaas asserts, 'very soon your house will betray you'.

Thinking with things

If we are to assume a greater uptake of healthcare at home to relieve pressures on current systems of delivery we must not simply develop solutions and focus research within the narrow boundaries of healthcare. Solutions will only be successful if they fit with the complexity of our lives therefore there is value in taking everyday experiences as a starting point.

The authors draw on the value of 'thinking with things' as a method to build understanding of the factors end-users identify as being important. Current work builds on a series of projects, led and now briefly described by the authors, that develops and utilises artefacts that are presented not as solutions, but as vehicles through which to engage people, promote discussion, to raise questions, challenge preconceptions, illicit information and generate in-depth data.

Significant in the 'future bathroom' project (Chamberlain and Yoxall 2012) was the recruitment of older people who were involved from the outset and in every stage of the research and product development. The approach broke down the hierarchical relationship often created between designer and user, academic researcher and user and adopted a respect for the user as expert, designing 'with' users and not just 'for' them. The older community lay researchers undertook home visits to older people living in the community and were able to empathise and gather more intimate stories than would have emerged through more traditional research methods (e.g. questionnaires) or if the younger academic research team had conducted the visits. Public exhibitions to open discussion around activities that are normally considered taboo were curated by author 1 (Figure 1). These insights revealed not only physical challenges within the bathroom as one ages but emotionally complex relationships in caring for others. Milligan (2009)

Figure 2. Stigmas a collection of furniture (author 1) that portrays and landscape of old age and part of the engaging series of exhibitions and workshops. Far left : 'This is a chair to sit on' that reflects declining cognitive processing. Far right : 'Adjustable chair' that reflects that the crude adjustments often made to accommodate declining physical ability.

describes how as ageing in place shifts care and support back toward the home and how informal carers are once again taking on many of the routine tasks of caring for the aging body. This includes much of the intimate and personal tasks involved in care such as washing and bathing, dressing, toileting and feeding the care recipient. Helping an older relative to perform normally personal and private acts such as bathing and toileting, for example, gives rise to transgressions of contemporary social taboos around care in western society – particularly cross sex care. Wiles (2003) claims these aspects of intimate care can involve considerable physical and emotional distress for both carer and care recipient.

Engagingaging (Chamberlain and Craig 2013) adopted a methodology that uses objects and artefacts (Figure 2) to stimulate and scaffold thinking, offering valuable vehicles through which the complexities of lives can be understood. It provided a theatre for conversation and the medium and method for data collection and created the conduit, through which societal assumptions relating to ageing could be made visible, explored and challenged. Building on methods developed within engagingaging the principles of the traditional exhibition were distilled into a format that was more flexible, accessible and inclusive.

'Exhibition in a box' (Chamberlain and Craig 2013) took the essence of the exhibition into a suitcase, a la

Duchamp that could be transported to diverse environs including the home. In doing so the home was transformed into the research arena, providing individuals with a tangible prompt to scaffold conversation.

These boxes comprised of everyday objects, photographs and textual material defined through the user-workshops undertaken in conjunction with the earlier large-scale exhibitions in 'engagingaging'. The objects were carefully selected to code, represent and prompt further discussion on themes that had emerged from earlier research. The objects could and did combine to create objective correlatives enabling participants to express emotional responses (Figure 3).

The present study, Insights into Telehealth and Care Technologies (inTaCT) undertaken by the authors utilises and further tests this methodology exploring participatory methods and approaches to engage people who are frequently under-represented in telehealth/telecare research by virtue of their age, ethnicity or socio-economic status, in meaningful ways. The strength of the critical artefact methodology is that the objects transcend boundaries of culture, language and age and whilst the objects remain unchanging the associations and emotions they prompt and the stories they elicit are dynamic and ever changing.

Figure 3. Exhibition in distilled into a box. Objects prompting meaningful insights into daily life.

Figure 4. HOSPITaBLe Chamberlain (selection from a collection): Top Left - Google aid. Top Right - IV Lamp. Bottom - Grande Commode.

This first phase of the research was a feasibility study, focusing particularly on the methods of engagement. Prior to recruitment of participants, ethical approval was obtained, following which posters and invitations describing the research and inviting people who might be interested in taking part in a workshop/focus group exploring technology were distributed through a number of voluntary and third sector organizations. These included: Age UK, the Churches Council for Community Care and the Chinese Elders.

In total thirty-two socially and ethnically diverse community dwelling older people were recruited. Individuals were invited to attend one of four workshops that were held in community venues and were facilitated by the research team. It was not a requirement for participants to be users of telehealth or telecare devices since the aim was to develop a broader understanding of participants' attitudes to digital products and devices. Each workshop lasted on average for two hours and participants were invited, in turn, to select and to respond to the objects contained within exhibition in a box. This data was analysed using framework analysis (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994). This enabled the development of a matrix of themes and related sub-topics from the data as well as identification of the links across themes, different participants and venues.

Refining the question

The present generation of home health technologies and products are predicated on the assumption that end-users have already embraced the shift in the healthcare paradigm from the hospital to their home. An assumption is also made that designing more aesthetically appealing products will automatically increase engagement in these products and technologies. However early findings of this present study suggests that acceptance of digital health solutions is more complex. Lee (Lee 2010) describes an alternative to the art-centred model of aesthetics that includes functional beauty. For example a coffee

maker may be aesthetically appreciable based on how well it makes coffee. However portraying aesthetic appeal in relation to products that deal with very private, intimate and traumatic matters of our illness may be more challenging to successfully achieve a signal of functional beauty. Lee draws on Heidegger's work and writes, 'in dwelling we do more than just construct our homes. We stay with them, care for them, turn them into places of meaning and meaning-making; our aesthetic sense of the home arises in this process'.

The initial findings from inTaCT have informed 'HOSPITaBLe' a collection of furniture created by author 1 (Figure 4) that embraces this complexity, and the artefacts through exhibition integrated with a series of community workshops aims to makes sense of this meaning. The artefacts present a hybrid ambiguous landscape each positioning metaphorical questions within the context of our future healthcare.

This work builds on the approach postulated by the designers who contributed to the *New Domestic Landscape* where Design is employed 'as a language to make commentary'. The artefacts created as part of HOSPITaBLe present questions rather than solutions. Dunne & Raby (in Koshinen et al 2011) support the notion that 'Design that asks carefully crafted questions and makes us think is just as important as design that solves problems or finds answers'. Mathematician and philosopher Henri Poincare is quoted to have declared, "The question is not, 'What is the answer?' The question is 'What is the question?'" (Licklider 1960).

There are undoubtedly many potential benefits to healthcare delivery at home. Delivery of care at home is not actually new and half a century ago house calls from the doctor were common but we have since witnessed a dramatic decline of this service. Home healthcare could extend care and provide greater and easier access for the care recipient allowing a more

customized and personal care package. Where social control has historically been the feature of hospitals we may see a rebalance of power when the patient is in the familiarity of their domestic environs. However more research is needed to explore how we negotiate the emotional complexity of what we understand as a home and what in more recent history has been institutionalized, a place for healthcare.

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Rationality and experientiality in product design

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Abstract Several studies on decision making allow us to observe that specialists use one of two systems to define their projects: rational (i.e., inferential or analytical system that operates by rules of reasoning, relatively affect-free) or experiential/intuitive (i.e., learning or automatic system that is intimately associated with affect). This paper presents a study that aimed to evaluate the reasoning process when making decisions of product designers in comparison to other professionals that work in the same field (i.e., Engineers and Architects). For this purpose, we used the Rational-Experiential Inventory (REI). Overall, our results show a significant difference between the engineers and the other professionals: they make decisions based on a more rational and less experiential system than architects and designers.

Keywords *Design decision making, Design intuition, Product design, Rational-Experiential Inventory*

Introduction

When confronted with several options, designers go through a cognitive process defined as judgment that makes it possible for them to make a choice between alternatives (Simon, 1996/1969). Several studies (e.g., Epstein, 1994) on judgment and decision making allow us to observe that people use one of two systems (dual-process theories) to define their projects: rational (i.e., inferential or analytical system that operates by rules of reasoning, relatively affect-free) or experiential/intuitive (i.e., learning or automatic system that is intimately associated with affect). Getting to know the process of how product designers make decisions is a way of understanding how their mental process works by learning if they rely more on their past experiences (experiential/intuitive system) or in their ability to reason about the subject (rational system) to make a choice while in a new project.

Assuming that the experiential/intuitive system is based on the person's experience and personality, professionals with different academic backgrounds may have unique profiles in the judgment and decision making process. Therefore, our goal is to look at the way professionals deal with their alternatives, trying to map their patterns of decision making. Designers, Engineers, and Architects, for example, develop projects that imply on making high impact decisions, and studies that try to compare how these individuals make decisions are not yet fully described.

Our hypothesis is that designers make decisions in a different way than other professionals. Design is known by its particular "design culture", which is commonly related to creativity and innovation. Therefore, designers may need to think in a more intuitive way than other professionals from areas in which structured problems that require solely reasoning are the most common issues in everyday practice. The goal of this research is to evaluate designers intuitive decision making process, in comparison to other professionals that work in

projects related to new products. For this purpose, we carried out a survey using the Rational-Experiential Inventory, described in the following section.

Methods

The research method consisted in an online survey. The instrument included questions related to the participants' demographic characteristics and the Rational-Experiential Inventory—REI (Pacini and Epstein, 1999). REI consisted of two main scales: Rationality ($\alpha = .85$), which corresponded to rational and analytical thinking style (e.g., "I am not a very analytical thinker") and Experientiality ($\alpha = .89$), which corresponded to intuitive and affective thinking style (e.g., "I believe in trusting my hunches"). Each scale included subscales of self-reported ability and engagement. Measures of ability refer to reports of high level of ability to either think logically and analytically (Rational Ability; $\alpha = .83$) or to rely on one's intuitive impressions and feelings (Experiential Ability; $\alpha = .80$). Measures of engagement refer to reliance on thinking in a logical/analytical manner (Rational Engagement; $\alpha = .67$) or on feelings (Experiential Engagement; $\alpha = .85$) when making decisions. Each scale is composed of 20 items (10 for ability and 10 for engagement) that are evaluated on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (definitely not true of myself) to 5 (definitely true of myself).

This was a descriptive, cross-sectional study with a convenience and snowball sampling. The sample was accessed through the researchers' networking and their peers. The only criterion for exclusion of the study was not being graduated in one of these pre-established areas or ever worked in the creation of new products.

Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics, Version 21.0. To test the differences between thinking styles, we conducted paired t-tests. To test differences between professional background (Designers x Engineers and Architects), we conducted

Univariate Analysis of Variance (ANOVAs). The dependent variable was the REI scales and subscales. Note that results were consistent even when age or gender was included as covariates in the ANOVAs, therefore, we'll only report main effects.

Results

Our sample consisted of 20 Designers, 30 Engineers, and 20 Architects. Overall, 64.3% of subjects were male. The mean age of subjects was 36.9 years ($SD = 12.0$). The average age for the Designers was 29.7 years ($SD = 3.8$), 41.2 years ($SD = 13.4$) for Engineers, and 37.7 years ($SD = 12.2$) for the Architects.

Overall results indicate that Designers and Engineers tend to rely more on Rational thinking ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.45$, and $M = 4.25$, $SD = 0.39$, respectively) than Experiential thinking ($M = 3.42$, $SD = 0.50$, and $M = 3.04$, $SD = 0.67$, respectively), $t(19) = 3.60$, $p = 0.002$, and $t(29) = 8.48$, $p < .001$, respectively.

In addition, Engineers showed a tendency to rely more on rational thinking style compared to Architects ($M = 3.94$, $SD = 0.60$), $F(2, 67) = 2.64$, $p = .079$, $MSE = 0.60$, $\eta^2_p = .073$ for the Rationality scale. This effect seems to be a result of their reliance on their ability to think logically (Rational Ability subscale), because Engineers ($M = 4.32$, $SD = 0.46$) had higher scores compared to Architects ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 0.71$), $F(2, 67) = 3.72$, $p = .029$, $MSE = 1.13$, $\eta^2_p = .10$.

Regarding Experientiality thinking style, our results show exactly the opposite, with Architects showing higher reliance on Experiential thinking style ($M = 3.77$, $SD = 0.46$) compared to Engineers; Designers showed a tendency to rely more on Experiential thinking ($M = 3.42$, $SD = 0.64$), $F(2, 67) = 10.01$, $p < .001$, $MSE = 3.28$, $\eta^2_p = .23$. This effect of greater reliance on Experiential thinking for Architects seems to be a result of both Experiential Ability and Engagement ($M = 3.79$, $SD = 0.48$, and $M = 3.74$, $SD = 0.58$, respectively) compared to Engineers ($M = 3.24$, $SD = 0.70$, and $M = 2.83$, $SD = 0.74$, respectively), $F(2, 67) = 5.64$, $p = .005$, $MSE = 1.91$, $\eta^2_p = .14$, and $F(2, 67) = 12.82$, $p < .001$, $MSE = 5.73$, $\eta^2_p = .28$, respectively. Designers reliance on Experiential thinking was significantly lower than Architects for Experiential Ability ($M = 3.34$, $SD = 0.45$) and higher than Engineers for Experiential Engagement ($M = 3.50$, $SD = 0.63$).

Conclusions

The goal of this research was to evaluate the process involved in judgment and decision making when developing a project in product design. Therefore we have compared thinking styles when designing a product from Designers, Engineers, and Architects who work in projects related to new products. Our findings suggested that all professionals make decisions using both rational and experiential systems, even though some (Designers and Engineers) might favor one process (Rational) over another (Experiential) as can be observed from paired comparisons.

A comparison between professions showed a cross-comparison for Architects, who favor Experientiality, and Engineers, who favor Rationality. Although Designers did not show a significant difference compared to Engineers and Architects, their scores on the Rationality scale and its subscales were somehow in between those of Architects and Engineers, suggesting they might be more likely to find a balance on their reliance on different thinking styles. That is, Designers showed that, when comes to judging options and making decisions, they rely on their analytical thoughts, but also use their past experiences and intuition.

This account suggests that people who can and do rely on rational thinking might also have irrational thoughts or perhaps are conflicted about what is rational and what is the value of experience. The way that each professional category processes information, evaluate available data and make decisions can be determinant in the way that the project and the product will be developed. For these reasons it is crucial to identify which decision-making systems are used while developing a new product.

Results of the current study should be considered in the context of certain methodological limitations. Firstly, this study used a cross-section design and should be considered exploratory. Secondly, our small sample size precludes other refinement processes such as more robust statistical analysis. Thirdly, these results are limited to this sample and should not be generalized. In spite of these limitations, the present study contributes in a significant way to the knowledge surrounding the relevance of evaluating the decision making processes. Fourthly, as with all voluntary surveys, there is the risk of self-selection bias. All the participants of our sample are Brazilians, which means that they have a similar demographic profile.

Table 1. Means and Standard Deviations of the Rational-Experiential Inventory (REI) Scales and Subscales.

Variable	Total Sample M(SD)	Designers M(SD)	Architects M(SD)	Engineers M(SD)	p
Rational	4.1(0.4)	4.0(0.4)	3.9(0.6)	4.2(0.3)	0.07
Engagement	4.1(0.4)	4.1(0.5)	3.9(0.5)	4.1(0.4)	0.27
Ability	4.1(0.5)	4.0(0.5)	3.9(0.7)	4.3(0.4)	0.04
Experiential	3.3(0.6)	3.4(0.4)	3.7(0.4)	3.0(0.6)	0.00
Engagement	3.2(0.7)	3.5(0.6)	3.7(0.5)	2.8(0.7)	0.00
Ability	3.4(0.6)	3.3(0.4)	3.7(0.4)	3.2(0.7)	0.00

The highlight of our study is that our online search of the literature didn't find other studies reporting REI-40 being used while comparing architects, engineers and designers, what prevents us of comparing our findings. The way that professionals make decisions warrants further investigation. Furthermore, it is important to understand if they would have better results when developing a new product if architects, engineers or designers used more of their rational or experiential system. Also, the understanding of the relation between the REI scales and emotionality could benefit from further investigation.

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Emotional cartography in design: A novel technique to represent emotional states altered by spaces

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Abstract Bio-signals as evaluation methods have been increasingly used for design and architectural research over the last few years. Understanding how environmental factors influence people's emotions by using psychophysiological tools represents an opportunity to improve design processes. As a part of an extensive exploration toward emotional maps, EDA signals were used. This preliminary work presents a study in which 12 participants explored an Immersive Virtual Environment (IVE) using a Head-Mounted Display while their sympathetic reaction was being registered. The response to the IVE (3 rooms designed to evoke neutrality, stress and calm states) was measured using both phasic electrodermal activity data gathered during IVE's exploration and psychometric response collected by post-questionnaire. Results show that the IVE evoked the expected emotional states to be measured, EDA-phasic was an appropriate tool to measure emotional states and the "emotional map" created by superimposing an emotional heatmap on the architectural layout confirms that it is possible to represent emotional states altered by spaces graphically.

Keywords *Emotional map, EDA, Virtual reality, Sympathetic reaction*

Introduction

Recently, researchers oriented to design and architecture have employed different psychophysiological signals in order to measure affective experience during simulated product interactions (Jenkins, Brown, & Rutterford, 2009; Laparra-Hernández et al, 2009). Numerous studies based on engineering approaches to automatically recognize emotions from physiological responses have been published (Goshvarpour, Abbasi & Goshvarpour, 2015). In all of them, the dataset was comprised of a set of features extracted from peripheral signals, such as electrocardiogram (ECG), galvanic skin response (GSR), electromyography (EMG) and others (Demangeot & Broderick, 2010). Design and architecture have started to use these physiological measures in product evaluations, in respect of the demanding need to generate mixed methodologies (Monestina et al, 2014).

This study focuses on the capacity of GSR signal to detect emotional states and the possibility to plot it. Emotional cartography (or emotional maps) is not a novel concept. This was popularized by Christian Nold

(2009). Environments affect people at cognitive and emotional levels. The idea of an emotional map is to place and plot these emotions elicited by spaces. Designers and architects have explored this concept before, developing different strategies to map the relation between places and emotions (Litteman, 2012; Fischer et al, 2014; Amilant-Szary and Mekjajian, 2015). However, Emotional Cartography remains a challenge because of the emotional characterization and tenuous relation with maps.

GSR is a bio-signal obtained by skin response which is also known as electrodermal activity (EDA). This signal refers to the variation of the electrical properties of the skin in response to sweat secretion. By applying a low constant voltage, the change in skin conductance (SC) can be measured non-invasively (Benedek & Kaernbach, 2010). EDA signals are related with the sympathetic nervous system. EDA has been used for more than a century as an indirect measurement of response to stimuli (CarretiéArangüena, 2011) since it is a signal which is rather easy to gather and understand, and the literature suggest that responds

Figure 1. Virtual Environments used in the study.

to threatening stimuli, as a reflection of arousal activity related with emotional states, and being the amplitude of the electrodermal response proportional to the “emotionality” of the eliciting stimuli (Fowles, 1980; Boucsein, 2012). It has already been used as a tool to assess environments, like Parson et al. (1998) who used it to evaluate differences in stress recovery between natural and urban environments, or to design elements such as colors (Jacobs and Hustmyer, 1974) and floorings (Laparra-Hernández et al, 2009). As Immersive Virtual Environments (IVE) have proved their ability to replicate real scenarios and the evoked emotional states (Rojas et al, 2015; Rodríguez et al, 2015), and have been previously used for EDA measurement (Felnhofer et al, 2015), an IVE was used to present the stimuli.

Materials and methods

Participants and apparatus

This study was conducted with 12 participants (4 female, 8 male) with ages ranging from 27 to 46 (M: 33.25; SD: 4.95) who did not receive any compensation for it. All participants reported normal or corrected vision, no heart rate problems and being familiar with VR systems.

The device used to acquire the EDA signal was a portable physiological wristband (E4 by Empatica©, www.empatica.com). EDA data was sampled at 4Hz (0.001 to 100 μ Siemens). To display VR environments, high immersive head mounted displays (HDM) were employed (Oculus DK2, www.oculus.com). This Head-Mounted Display (HMD) is 7-inches wide with 1920x1080 pixels resolution split between both eyes, yielding 960x1080 pixels per eye. Sennheiser HD215 headphones were also used with a frequency response of 12 - 22000 Hz. The computer which was used to run all software has a core i5 (3.4 GHz) CPU with 8GB of RAM, and a graphical-card AMD RADEON r9-255 Series GPU (2 GB). A gamepad was used for user navigation.

Stimuli

The IVE was made using SketchUp® (v2016) and exported to graphical development platform using Unity 3D® (v5.3) for displaying in Oculus DK2. The designed environment contained 28.834 polygons and 25 textures. It consisted of five rooms; two as entry and exit points and the ones between them were designed to evoke three emotional states: Neutrality, Stress and Calm (see Figure 1). Both stress and calm rooms were designed following evidence-based guidelines to achieve the required emotional states: the level of enclosure and outside views (Chang, 2005), ceiling height (Meyers-Levy, & Zhu, 2007), sharp or curved contours (Vartanian et al, 2013) and gaudy (red, black) or soft colors (blue, lilac) (Yildirim et al, 2011; Jalil et al, 2012). Sound factors were included to increase emotional states inside rooms; traffic and mechanical sounds in stress room and nature sounds in the calm room were added (Alvarsson, Wiens, & Nilsson, 2010; Valenti et al, 2012). Due to the VR tendency to increase stress levels (Mon Williams, Warm, & Rushton, 1993), the calm room was placed at the end of the path.

Procedure

The participants were asked to sit in front of a computer with a gamepad, headphones and the HMD at dimly-lit laboratory room. The instructions were given while participants were putting these devices and the E4 wristband on. Before starting the task, a baseline was conducted to equalize participants to a similar emotional state. The main task designed for this study was a free exploration through the rooms with no time limit. The participants started the exploration in the entry point before walking to the neutral room. The task ends when participants cross the calm room to the exit point (see Figure 2). The participants' movements in IVE were tracked by a script running under the graphical development platform, in order to export position and time references into a data base. A post-questionnaire with basic demographic questions and 7-point Likert-scales about emotional state from Russell, Weiss, & Mendelsohn (1989) was fulfilled. Three questions were

Figure 2. Top view of the complete VR environment.

asked to rate the levels of pleasure, arousal and stress. The scales used have a double purpose: to validate the designed environments (neutral, stressful, and relaxing spaces) and to find possible correlations between psychometric response and EDA bio-signal.

Data analysis and results

The registered EDA signal was pre-processed and analyzed with an EDA analysis toolbox (Ledalab® V3.4.8, www.ledalab.de) running under Matlab 2012a. Pre-processing consisted of a visual diagnostic of artefacts and their corrections. A continuous decomposition analysis (CDA, Benedek and Kaernbach, 2010) was used to clean the signal and to detect a phasic component associated to ambient discrete stimuli caused by abrupt increases in skin conduction (Dawson, 2001). The phasic signal of every subject was exported and synchronized in a temporal line. Once the EDA-phasic signal was ready, both data bases (EDA-phasic, and the position registered by script), were introduced to Matlab script to synchronize and create a heat map representation.

To control inter-subject variations, EDA-phasic data was unitarized between 0 and 1 for each subject using 0 as the lowest score and 1 as the highest score for sympathetic activation. In order to ensure the quality of the representation, we considered the following assumptions: 1) if participants crossed the same point in space, the maximum EDA-phasic data would be taken between points (individual maps were made to corroborate the data); and 2) after analysing all the subjects, an overall heat map was made by plotting sympathetic activation means only if, at least, 25% of the sample (three participants) crossed the same point in the space.

The heat map representation is shown in Figure 3. It should be clarified that this kind of heat map represents the highest unitary EDA in red colour and the lowest data in blue colour. However, in this

representation the blank space does not represent low data for sympathetic activation, but rather that data level activation is unknown because it does not comply with the two previous considerations. The results of unitary EDA means and data obtained from questionnaire show in Table 1.

A descriptive analysis is shown in Table 1. Psychometric and EDA data was treated with Z-standardized means to simplify comparative interpretation.

Shapiro-Wilk Test revealed that the distributions were not normal. Kruskal-Wallis Test found significant differences between stress and calm rooms both in questionnaire and EDA responses (Pleasure $p=0.000$, Arousal $p=0.000$, Stress $p=0.000$ and EDA-phasic $p=0.033$) and no significant differences neither between neutral and relax rooms nor between neutral and stress rooms. Spearman's Rho Test was used to find out bivariate correlations within variables, showing statistically significant inverse correlation between EDA-Pleasure (coef= -0.379 $p=0.023$) and non-significant correlation between EDA-Arousal (coef= 0.169 $p=0.235$) and EDA-Stress (coef= 0.221 $p=0.195$).

Table 1. Statistics descriptive or rooms' perception and EDA data.

Room	Pleasure	Arousal	Stress	EDA unitarized
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
Neutral	0.25 (0.54)	-0.33 (0.71)	-0.67 (0.56)	-0.025 (1.280)
Stress	-1.18 (0.39)	0.98 (0.73)	1.16 (0.53)	0.533 (0.809)
Calm	0.93 (0.47)	-0.64 (0.73)	-0.49 (0.62)	-0.508 (0.546)

Figure 3. Emotional map: red color shows the highest unitary EDA score and blue color, the lowest.

Discussion

In this study, different spaces, evidence-based designed, achieved to elicit the expected emotional responses in the participants, as the questionnaire endorses. Subsequently, recording psychophysiological response while tracking spatial location throughout the IVE was possible. The signal could be processed to obtain solid data and statistical analysis found significant differences in psychophysiological responses between stress and calm rooms highlighting an inverse correlation between EDA signal and pleasure.

Electrodermal activity seems to be adequate to create emotional representations in correlation to the pleasure generated by space (Kreibig, 2010) contributing to previous emotional cartography research charted by Nord (2009), Littenan (2012), Fischer et al (2014) or Amilant-Szary & Mekjajian (2015).

This is a preliminary study with a reduced sample size in order to obtain experience in conducting a future study with a larger sample size and better analysis methods. EDA data showed substantially different measurements between participants (magnitude order) that requires normalized statistics for comparison. A criterion must be considered to select the minimum number of participants to represent in a map.

Psychophysiological environment effects were marked by individual perception of participants and the creative criteria of the designer. This study included multiple variables (color, geometry, heights, decorations and sounds) to guarantee sympathetic activation. A disadvantage can be created to ignore the

whole influence of one of each of these aesthetic elements in the environment. Nevertheless, this is not the aim of this study.

Conclusion

The EDA signal has potential to be considered as an essential psychological tool to quantify emotional states inside environments and the development of emotional cartographic. This study exposed a novel technique to represent emotional states. The proposal of our technique is to help and promote the objective quantification of subjective experiences and locate the point where this occurs. Future studies aim to bring the results further by using other psychophysiological signals like ECG. Being able to easily plot emotional states in architectural layouts opens a range of possibilities: evaluating the isolated impact of design elements in mood (color, vegetation...), assessing existing places for critical points or designing task-oriented spaces (e.g. relaxation, creativity...). That is, designing better places.

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Autoethnographic account of 2L Finnish learning. Disambiguation of language

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Abstract After the recent refugee crisis Europe was plagued with anti-immigration policies and doubts about the effectiveness of immigrant integration programs; Finland was no exception. Integration programs include teaching of the official language, however not to advanced levels. This leaves foreigners as basic communicators —with poor language skills— and low profile candidates for mainstream job markets slowing social integration. This paper integrates the authors' previous work about an online Finnish language learning system —ideation, construction and testing— created to resolve foreigners' unmet needs. The data presented here, is the result of a trial performed on such system and presented as an autoethnographic study focusing on the emotional implications and dual-role of a learner and researcher. Results show how online 2L systems help learners with ambiguous situations —linguistic and social— by lowering anxiety with indirect interaction. Future studies on possible solutions include the design of metacognitive strategies and reading/writing tools for 2L Finnish for specific purposes.

Keywords *Autoethnography, Language-learning, Social-integration, Ambiguity in language*

Introduction

Social phenomena such as immigration have unavoidable consequences —such as social and economic instability—. The most recent refugee crisis from Syria has affected Europe and raised debates on anti-immigration policies and integration programs for foreign population. Finland alone has received over 30 000 refugees by the end of 2015¹ of which many may be candidates for integration programs and Finnish language courses (2L hereafter). Finnish language is part of the Uralic linguistic group, unrelated to other linguistic families and origin unknown. Finnish language is a key part of Finnish identity; teaching it to foreign population is of relevance to preserve this living cultural feature.

Paradoxically, 2L Finnish language integration courses only offer beginner to mid-level² courses. Personal experience as a learner —with governmental institutions and private courses— and earlier studies (Rodriguez-Kaarto & Hahn, 2014) confirmed the lack of advanced courses offered by the Ministry of Education or Employment; private custom-tailored courses are a costly alternative.

In consequence, after complying with these courses learners remain basic communicators —with poor writing and reading skills— making them low profile candidates for the Finnish mainstream job markets. This has taxing consequences on their wellbeing and social development; since poor language skills are a strong reason for unemployment and low wages among foreign population in Finland (Yleisradio, 2012; Elonen & Wooley, 2014). In search for solutions to advance 2L learners, this study has searched for

possible online solutions. This paper presents autoethnographic results of a trial for an online learning system in Finnish (Rodriguez-Kaarto & Hahn, 2015); with special focus on the role of emotions and disambiguation processes in language learning. Research questions are:

RQ1: Why is autoethnography a reliable and adequate method to discuss emotional ambiguity in language?

RQ2: What are the emotional aspects of 2L learning?

Theoretical review

This section briefly reviews the most popular language-learning theories that explain how we acquire language and its emotional implications. In addition, a brief review on Reflective Autoethnography methods applied in this study is also revised.

Cognitive and ecological approaches for L2 learning

The following language theories are the basis for our online system for 2L acquisition (Hahn & Rodriguez-Kaarto, 2015; Rodriguez-Kaarto & Hahn, 2015). **The**

- 1 The Finnish Immigration Services, 2016.
- 2 According to the Common European Framework of References for Languages (CEFR), A1 is the beginners or breakthrough level and C2 corresponds to proficient users, with two stages for each level. B2 (advanced-intermediate) is the highest level offered in *Finnish for foreigners* courses. http://www.coe.int/t/dg4/linguistic/Source/Framework_EN.pdf

cognitive approach (Krashen, 1982) assumes that learning takes place linearly, coherently and progressively through comprehensible linguistic inputs ($i + 1$); learners advance step-by-step and complexify in their use of the language. **The ecological approach** (van Lier, 2000; 2004; 2010) takes learning as a complex, dynamic and non-linear progression of knowledge through linguistic affordances in an environment full of semiotic possibilities; learners interact with *More Knowledgeable Others* that scaffold them to the *Zone of Proximal Development*. In both cases, these theories emphasize the role of emotional wellbeing as crucial for 2L learning — affective filters (Krashen, 1981; 2002), and learner's self-concept (van Lier, 2000; 2004; 2010)—. Additionally, Fredrickson and Branigan (2005, p. 315) focus on how positive emotions *amplify* cognitive capacities given the right motivation. Positive emotions in 2L language learning, expand the learners' "thought-action" repertoire —the ability to relate broader concepts— making them more flexible and empathic learners (Fredrickson and Branigan, 2005, p. 315).

Methodology: Reflective autoethnography

As part of ethnographic research, autoethnography is recognized as a method for extracting data from self-reflective observations of the researcher while being a member of the group under study. There are different types of autoethnography: a) *evocative ethnography* with focus on the personal interpretation of a phenomenon (Ellis & Bochner, 2000), b) *interpretive* whereby research is carried out as a "biographical studies of experiences and performance of a person" (Denzin, 2014) and the one applied to this study c) *analytic autoethnography* (Anderson, 2006).

In analytic autoethnography, Leon Anderson (2006) introduces five key aspects. 1) **Complete Member Researcher** (CMR): the researcher is "a complete member in the social world under study" (p.379). The CMR role is of a "double-viewer" —researcher and member—, CMRs are expected to analyze both, the participants' common interpretations of phenomena —diverse among members— and her own (p.380). 2) **Reflexive Autoethnography** is the capacity to be analytical of our connection with the research; mindful of the on going information exchange between the group and us (p.380-382). 3) Autoethnographic studies collect data of phenomena that involves us inside the group; therefore, being a **Visible and Active Researcher in the Text** and report personal experiences and feelings is part of the key data. This means that researcher may write in first person using "I" or "my" while reporting data. 4) Additionally, to document how the researcher's participation affects and "transforms social understanding and relations" (p.385) is relevant since in autoethnographic studies our **Dialogues With Informants Beyond the Self** are part of the data. 5) Finally, Anderson calls for a **Commitment to an Analytic Agenda**, referring to "empirical data to gain insight into a broader set of social phenomena than those provided by the data" (p.387).

Collection of data

This section is an account of the open trial period of Finnish101.fi —an online 2L learning system for advanced learning— carried out in December 2015. The first trial of Finnish101.fi aimed to test how learners could improve their use of language through Self-regulated learning (SRL). This method derives from educational psychology, where the learners are active developers of their own metacognitive strategies for self-improvement regardless of external factors (Schunk & Zimmerman, 1998; Zimmerman, 1998; Zimmerman & Schunk, 2001; Chamot 2014). SRL provides cognitive framework to define concepts (Big Ideas) and frame relevant questions (Essential questions). Learners were recommended to apply SRL techniques to Content Based Learning (CBL), which meant they should choose the content they wanted to work with in the target language (Kaufman & Crandall, 2005; Chamot, 2009).

My daily participations as a researcher and learner consisted in detail on writing my own content, revising posts, comments, e-mails or chat conversations and keep motivation high among learners. A record of every interaction, production and insight gained —as a participant and researcher— is kept in the internal logs of the sites database.

Finnish101.fi overview

Finnish101.fi is constructed with free open software, providing functionality yet a rigid interface. It offered helpful links and aggregation functions for videos, images, forums, tags and chat.

This online system follows a set of principles and strategies (Hahn & Rodriguez-Kaarto, 2014; Rodriguez-Kaarto & Hahn 2015) drawn from 2L language learning theories (Krashen, 1981; 2002) (van Lier, 2000; 2004; 2010) in our previous studies; emphasizing active learning and interaction with *More Knowledgeable Others* (Vygotsky, 1997) to scaffold learners to *Zones of Proximal Development* (Vygotsky, 1997). The system comprises four learning modules (Observation, Writing, Reading and Speech and Interaction) and a Dictionary-Phrase bank tool to holistically link different areas of language learning (Rodriguez-Kaarto & Hahn, 2015). The site is a platform where learners create their own content in the target language, share and discuss with other learners/peers. By doing so, they broaden their knowledge of the chosen topic and the target language.

Participants: learners and peers

The trial recruited ten foreign Finnish students from basic to mid-advanced level and ten Finnish native speakers to use the system for three weeks. The call for participations —issued in social media circles— invited foreign participants (*learners* hereafter) to interact in the system using the target language for an average time of 60-90 minutes daily. It requested the participation and interaction of Finnish native speakers (*peers* hereafter) for 60 minutes daily under the same circumstances. The participation time equated the amount of hours of a "study credit" in a regular Finnish for foreigners course —as explained by Finnish language teachers—. Our participants were

Figure 1. Finnish101 front page.

from different universities in Finland and held different degrees (i.e. masters to post-doctoral degrees). The rest took part as independent learners — whose identities or language level could be verified—.

Collection of data

Participants initially created a user profile with their basic information (i.e. language skills, professional and academic interests). As an administrator and a user, I monitored learners' login times, participations and topics during the three weeks of the trial; the analysis of the data took place between February and April 2016.

My own participations involved extensive online search, writing and editing on topics relevant to my research. I followed Self-regulated learning³ (Chamot, 2014); searched for related material in Finnish, translated keywords and posed Essential Questions in discussion forums. Since I had a special interest to write posts using self-regulated learning and discuss topics relevant to my research, all posts involved extensive online search, writing and editing beyond my skill level.

Discussion of findings

The data analyzed are samples of discussion forums and posts from the trial. Feedback from the participants was collected online through a brief questionnaire at the beginning and end of the trial. Their feedback and discussions made evident the adequacy of autoethnographic methods for analyzing emotional implications in 2L learning.

Emotional aspects of 2L online learning

The process of 2L learning is an emotional one. Abundant research points towards anxiety and negative emotions as causes involved in slow 2L learning. As a learner, I observed that online learning

systems may drop learners' anxiety by providing indirect personal interactions; relieve the frustration from awkward face-to-face encounters. Online 2L systems may provide a suitable environment for advanced learners to connect, carefully research the language and produce content. Additionally, online systems with discussion forums offer a good linguistic resource where the learners can compare different structures and writing styles. Learners' feedback pointed out that during the introductions she "could see different ways and expressions to talk about 'same' thing." (from electronic communication, November 30th 2015).

In my case, posting was not without pressure; a step-by-step Self-regulated learning felt too strict and not spontaneous. However, results were clear with strings-of-words⁴ and vocabulary augmentation. Reflecting on the trial, I realize that learners might also have perceived Self-regulated learning too rigid and so didn't follow it. Feedback from learners revealed they wanted to improve their use of Finnish, however not for specific purposes. As doctoral students they produce work only in English, so the topics during the trial seem casual and unrelated to professional or academic endeavors. I concluded that independent learning needs more than just the motivation to improve in 2L. Emotional investment in 2L is crucial for advancement (Krashen, 1981; 2002)

- 3 Self-Regulated learning: Independent learners for 2L draw out *Big Ideas* from a topic of choice. They formulate *Essential Questions* which they answer in the target language using *Keywords* previously defined by them (Chamot, 2014).
- 4 *Strings-of-words* refers to the order in which words are placed in a sentence.

Figure 2. Image composite of the original Eppu Normaali “Murhelisten laulujen maa” video (upper three images) with images of the cover version (below) depicting Finnish people with diverse ethnic backgrounds.

(van Lier, 2000; 2004; 2010). Therefore, systems like Finnish101 need learners in dire need to improve in their 2L (i.e. non-English speaking learners).

Autoethnography of a 2L learner

Reflexive awareness in Autoethnography poses complexity when researchers need to make sense of two strains of —apparently— contradicting data. As a learner and researcher, the information gathered gave insights on our needs and lack of metacognitive strategies for 2L. Most learners cannot compose texts in Finnish without structuring it first in English as commented by a learner “I can’t construct correct structures [...] and use correct form of the Finnish words, though I used Google translator to help me” (from electronic communication, November 30th 2015). This common practice perpetuates our structural mistakes since our texts usually “come out wrong or funny” (i.e. the Google translate effect). Through this study I also became aware of flaws in Finnish101.fi design and need for peer/learner communication protocols. This would have enabled peers to correct our texts openly. Participants expressed their opinion on this shortcoming over feedback: “It’s a bit difficult to start correcting people’s writing, it feels impolite especially if not asked for directly” (from electronic communication, November 30th 2015); or as expressed by a learner “I am not sure if I am using the proper words [...] I wish I could ask someone when I am puzzled” (from electronic communication, November 30th 2015).

The reliability/adequacy of autoethnographic methods in 2L learning lays on the fact that 2L learning produces cognitive and emotional data difficult to understand as a sole observer. To reflect on this

process raises awareness of the tacit knowledge gathered in practice. It helps us “make new sense of the situations of uncertainty or uniqueness” that we encounter (Schön 1983, p. 61). The unique sense of accomplishment after producing a well-written text are the types of motivation learners need to continue their exploration of the target language.

Disambiguation in 2L learning

Disambiguation in this paper is taken as: i) the act of clarifying literal meanings of words and ii) removing uncertainty of their use in different social circumstances —contextual meanings and cultural representations—. Such are the cases of polysemy and contextual variations, common conundrums in 2L. Words that have over one meaning or strings-of-words that vary according to the context are difficult for learners to decipher. During the trial I posted a video of a cover song for a Finnish 80s classic pop-song; the original version talks about Finnish lifestyle and ideals of the 80s (i.e. male roles). We discussed about the second versions’ meaning in our forum, where people with various ethnic backgrounds sang solemnly about *Finnishness* (in the midst of anti-immigration discussions). Many words needed translation and the topic ignited discussions on some deeper cultural implications and disambiguation of contextual meanings; the shift between an original humorous version vs. a new serious and touching one.

Conclusion

This autoethnographic study revealed how online 2L systems can lower learners’ anxiety and possible frustration from face-to-face encounters by providing indirect personal interactions. By providing a suitable environment for interaction, research and production

of content, an online 2L system provides good resources for learners to compare linguistic structures and writing styles; disambiguate and negotiate contextual meanings. This study reinforced the statement that emotional investment is crucial for independent learning. The reliability and adequacy of autoethnography in 2L, lays on the fact that 2L learning is a cognitive and emotional process difficult to understand as a sole observer. Autoethnographic methods raise awareness of the emotional data and allow researchers to gain insights on their learning strengths and weaknesses. This gives a wider overview of what may be required to improve learner's use of 2L. Future research will concentrate on improving Finnish101.fi and develop tools for writing and reading comprehension, aural exercises and cultural observations.

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A framework of technology-supported emotion measurement

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Abstract Emotion measurement is a vital aspect for new product development and product improvements (see e.g. P. Desmet & Schifferstein, 2012). Nowadays, new technological devices, data mining, and social media offer many opportunities to invigorate design research. This paper tries to combine both aspects by exploring the question, how new technologies can be utilized for emotion-focused design research. The range of applicable technologies spans from eye-tracking, to EEG measuring, to semi-automated facial expression recognition in photographs or texts based on data mining technologies or crowdsourcing, etc. Furthermore, many traditional technologies for emotion tracking are becoming smaller and mobile, which allows also in-field research (e.g. mobile EEG headsets). Triangulating different data sources might result in new insights and improve user research significantly. This paper provides an overview of related literature indicating the current state of emotion measurement in the design field, and presents a framework that outlines possible new approaches utilizing new technologies. Thus, this work might contribute as a source of inspiration for other researchers to develop new research approaches for technology-supported emotion measurement.

Keywords *Research methodologies and methods, New technologies, User research, Emotion measurement, Science theory*

Introduction

The possibility to measure people's emotions can be useful for design research in two ways: The emotions people experience when interacting with a product can provide valuable insights about problems, flaws, and difficulties, but also pleasures and enjoyments that this particular product triggers. In so-called usability tests, researchers can investigate these emotional reactions and hence improve the product. This sort of emotion research is mainly conducted by marketing or user experience (UX) experts and usually happens in laboratory situations to exclude other possible influences on the emotional responses. On the other hand, context-related emotions measured in a realistic environment can provide valuable insights about users' tacit feelings, wishes, needs, and concerns, and hence result in ideas for new product development and innovations (P. Desmet & Schifferstein, 2012).

Although both approaches are important and reasonable for design research, the context-related emotion measurement seems to be of more relevance

for design research, because it produces more authentic data, which is gathered directly in the field and in the situation, rather than in the laboratory or having to be recalled later-on through a questionnaire. Moreover, this context-related research might result in new design insights, which open up new product or service design opportunities.

However, our literature search reveals that design research on context-related emotions is still in its beginnings, which can be partly explained by the relatively complex and obtrusive equipment that used to be necessary for emotional measurement. However, nowadays new technological advancements resulted in devices that are becoming more mobile, wearable, unobtrusive, and affordable, which allows also for ethnographic studies in the field, to gain real-time insights on people's emotions while they are actually in that particular situation. Moreover, such technological advancements also lead to emerging societal phenomena, such as life-logging and fitness-tracking. These phenomena, along with the ubiquitous presence of smartphones and the rise of social media,

offer new opportunities for design research, and emotion research in particular.

This survey paper presents a literature-based overview of the current state of research about technology-supported emotion measurement. The main contribution of this paper is a framework that categorizes different possible approaches and types of emotion measurement. This framework will hopefully inspire other researchers within the Design & Emotion community to utilize such technologies for their own research and might help to identify the right technology for their own research projects.

Related work

Our literature search focused on studies about technology-based emotion measurement. We limited the search criteria to a) the top 14 design journals (based on Gemser, de Bont, Hekkert, & Friedman, 2012), b) relevant journals from sociology, psychology, medicine, and computer science (based on an impact factor greater than 1), and c) papers published in the previous Design & Emotion conferences. The searched databases were Web of Science and Scopus, using the following search terms: emotion, cognition, behaviour, neuromarketing, neuroscience, emotion measurement, and psychophysiological measurement. In addition, reference lists of review articles were manually searched for further literature on the topic (backward and forward citation analysis).

These searches resulted in a total of 72 papers identified as relevant for our review. For inclusion in the review, papers had to deal with measuring emotions using neuro-physiological, observational, self-report or physiological methods. We used matrices to summarize the results and clustered them into thematic groups.

A detailed literature review of these 72 papers would exceed the scope and word limit of this short paper, which is why we summarize only the main findings here.

Eight papers can be categorized as survey papers, which provided overviews of emotion research in different areas and with different contexts, for example: Poels and Dewitte (2006) provide an overview of methods for emotion research in the advertising field over the past 20 years. They distinguish between automated (unconscious) “low-order” emotions (e.g. pleasure) and cognitive (conscious) “high-order” emotions (such as the fear to lose one’s job). Their findings indicate that most studies on emotion research in this area were conducted in unnatural laboratory situations, with the goal to test existing products or marketing campaigns. Mauss and Robinson (2009) present an overview of emotion research. They distinguish between 1) self-report measures, 2) autonomous measures (reactions of the autonomic nervous system, such as sweat or blood pressure), 3) startle response magnitude measures (reflexes like muscle tensing or eye blinks), 4) brain states measures (EEG or Neuroimaging/fMRI), and 5) behaviour (vocal, facial and whole body behaviour). Kanjo, Al-Husain, & Chamberlain (2015) present a

state-of-the-art overview of currently available emotion monitoring tools. Lopatovska and Arapakis (2011) review literature on the theories of emotions, methods for studying emotions, and their role in human information behavior, but without a specific focus on technologies. Rebelo, Noriega, Duarte, & Soares (2012) present an overview of emotion measurement tools and techniques. Based on their findings that most studies were conducted in laboratory settings they propose the use of Virtual Reality (VR) and Virtual Environments (VE) to substitute real in-field research. Desmet (2015) discusses the phenomenon of mood in various dimensions. For example, he presents an overview of several innovative technologies to assess mood, as well as the influence of technology itself on people’s mood. Wrigley, Gomez, & Popovic (2010) present an overview of methods and basic technologies to measure emotions in qualitative research. They distinguish between observation techniques, think-aloud protocols, questionnaires, diaries, interviews, and they discuss advantages and challenges for each category.

From the analyzed 72 papers, 12 were from the field of Medicine (Psychiatry, Neurology, Neuroscience), 18 from Psychology and/or Marketing, and 34 from the fields of Computer Science, Electrical Engineering, and HCI. Only 8 papers were directly related to design, new product development, and design engineering. The used methods for emotion measurement can be differentiated into three categories: 21 papers mainly used neuro-physiological methods (body responses such as brain activity, skin conductance, pulse rate, etc.), 19 papers used observational techniques (facial expressions, gestures, etc.), and 11 papers used self-reporting methods (questionnaires, interviews, diaries, etc.). The remaining 13 papers used mixed method approaches (e.g. physiological measures that were additionally validated by self-reports). Only four studies were conducted in real-life environments; a fifth one used a Virtual Reality environment to simulate a real environment. The remainder of the studies were conducted in laboratory settings. Only one paper (Behoora & Tucker, 2015) addresses data mining as a possible approach for emotion measurement combined with commercially available motion sensors (Kinect).

Thus, our literature research shows that technological opportunities for emotion research are not much implemented in design research and design projects, but are rather limited to the fields of HCI, Computer Science, Medicine, Psychology, and Marketing. Almost all of the studies were conducted in laboratory settings, which demonstrates a significant prospective potential for ethnographic and in-field design research.

Framework of technology-based emotion measurement

Desmet and Schifferstein (2012) distinguish between four types of emotion measurement, based on: 1) behavioral actions (such as type and pace of movement), 2) expressive reactions (such as facial or vocal expressions, tone of voice, postures, and

Figure 1. Framework of technologies according to the four categories of emotional measurement.

gestures), 3) physiological reactions (such as heart rate, pulse, pupil dilatation, or sweating), and 4) subjective experiences and (verbalized) feelings. They give a brief overview of research methods in general emotion research.

Thoring, Mueller, and Badke-Schaub (2015) present an overview of technological devices, software tools, social media, and data mining technologies, and suggest opportunities how these could be utilized to invigorate design research in terms of data collection and data analysis, but they do not focus on emotion research in particular.

We use the two above mentioned frameworks and classifications to develop these further into a new framework, which is focusing on the technological opportunities for *emotion* research. Our definition of the term technology is not limited to hard- and software, but includes also concepts and phenomena that are based on a technological infrastructure, such as social media or crowdsourcing. We also present technologies that are not mainly focusing on emotion research, because the triangulation of different data sources facilitates the interpretation of emotional responses. For example, measuring people's emotions with a mobile EEG scanner in relation to their various locations (measured through GPS data) might indicate the influence of the environment on that person's wellbeing.

We aligned different technologies according to the four types of emotion measurement: 1) behavior, 2) expression, 3) physiology, and 4) experience. In the following section we describe the different technologies briefly, per category, and summarize the results in a table overview (Table 1). Figure 1 shows the resulting framework of technology-based emotion measurement.

Technologies for behavior measurement

Behavior means the more or less conscious activity of a person as a reaction to an emotion, for example, the behavior of *running* as a reaction to *fear* (P. Desmet & Schifferstein, 2012). Such behavior can mainly be measured through technologies that observe people's movements either visually (video cameras, drones), or data-driven (GPS, indoor positioning). Specific gestures can also be interpreted as conscious behavior (e.g. hitting someone or something), which can be measured through motion sensors (Kinect, Wii). Cameras that automatically take pictures based on sensor changes, such as environmental temperature, light, movement, etc. (e.g. Autographer) can also provide insights about people's behavior in relation to their respective context and environment. Fitness trackers capture metadata about the wearer, such as step count, running, swimming, etc. and hence can reveal insights on that person's behavior. Social media can partly be utilized to extract insights about people's emotion-related behavior, for example by analyzing published

videos in YouTube. Social Network Analysis can be used to detect relationships (and hence dependencies) between people, which can also be interpreted in terms of emotional behavior. Eye Tracking can reveal external causes for specific actions (either in the environment or when interacting with a product or website).

Technologies for expression measurement

Expression means the mainly unconscious reactions to emotions that can be inferred from facial expressions, tone and volume of voice, and gestures. These can best be measured through tools that deliver photo, video, or audio data. On the one hand, these can be captured through recording devices (cameras, voice recorders),

or through self-published data in social media (e.g. YouTube movies). And on the other hand, there are tools available that facilitate the interpretation process (e.g. data mining, crowdsourcing, etc.). Motion sensors, such as Nintendo Wii or Microsoft Kinect, can be used to measure bodily gestures. Not only people in real-time, but also people's pictures in social media channels, such as Instagram or YouTube, can be analyzed for facial and bodily expressions.

Technologies for physiology measurement

Physiology measurement usually requires sophisticated sensor-based equipment. Nowadays, such equipment has become affordable, unobtrusive, wireless, and wearable, which allows for in-field and

Table 1. Overview of technologies aligned with type of emotional measurement.

Technology	Examples / Link	Behavior	Expression	Physiology	Experience
Fitness Tracker	www.fitbit.com www.nikeplus.com withings.com	+		+	
Experience Sampling	www.pacoapp.com				+
Smartpen	www.livescribe.com				+
Kapture	www.kaptureaudio.com				+
Autographer	www.autographer.com	+			
GoPro	www.gopro.com	+	+		
Drones	www.parrot.com www.3dr.com	+			
Google Glass	www.google.com/glass	+	+		
Eye Tracking (mobile/stationary)	www.tobii.com www.eyetracking-glasses.com www.smivision.com	+		+	
Facial Expression Recognition	www.emotient.com www.affectiva.com www.nviso.ch		+	+	
EEG Measurement	www.emotiv.com			+	
Skin Conductor	www.biopac.com			+	
Motion Sensors	www.xbox.com (Kinect) www.nintendo.de (Wii)	+	+		
GPS / Indoor Positioning	www.indoo.rs www.infsoft.de www.indooratlas.com www.redpin.org www.goindoor.co	+			
Facebook	www.facebook.com		(Photo)		+
Twitter	www.twitter.com		(Photo)		+
Instagram	www.instagram.com		+		
Youtube	www.youtube.com	(+)	+		(+)
Image Data Mining	www.rapidminer.com www.knime.org www.projectoxford.ai		+		
EEG Signal Processing	sccn.ucsd.edu/eeglab			+	
Sentiment Mining	www.sentiment140.com				+
Social Network Analysis	gephi.org	+			
Amazon Mechanical Turk	www.mturk.com		+		+
QDA Analysis Software	www.dedoose.com www.maxqda.com www.atlasti.com www.qsrinternational.com		+		+
Data Management Software	www.imotions.com	+	+	+	+

remote research. EEG scanners and related software can turn brainwaves into meaningful data. Life-logging movements result in millions of people tracking their own bodily functions, such as heart rate, pulse, temperature, etc. Infrared cameras can indicate skin temperature. And certain eye-tracking glasses can measure pupil dilatation.

Technologies for experience measurement

Experiences or “feelings” are usually verbalized and self-reported by the participants. Specific Experience Sampling applications (e.g. PACO) allow to send questionnaires to people via their smartphones. Thus, the emotions can be measured in real-time, while people are in the respective situation. Written or spoken texts (e.g. from Twitter feeds or Facebook pages) can be analyzed for emotional indications, either manually, or through data mining (sentiment mining) technologies, or by utilizing a crowdsourcing approach. Sophisticated audio recording devices also facilitate this process, for example by providing time buffers so that no important information will get lost (Kapture), or automated matching of written notes to audio timestamps (Smartpen).

Figure 1 outlines the categorization of different technologies regarding their capabilities to measure emotions according to the four types of emotion measurement.

Discussion

The presented framework of technology-supported emotion measurement (Figure 1) is considered a first attempt to classify currently available technologies according to their potential for facilitating emotion research in the design field. The classification is intended to help researchers identify the appropriate technology for their respective research question. However, the borders between the suggested four categories are not always sharp. For example, a measured smile can be either an unconscious expression, or a conscious behavior, which might not be differentiated by the used technology. And similarly, a specific technology, like a video camera, can be used to measure different types of emotions (behavior, expression, or even experience). Thus, the suggested framework is only a guideline and can be adapted as the researcher sees fit.

One of the main contributions of utilizing several technologies is the possibility for triangulation of different data sources. Complementing the data from one source (e.g. emotions measured through a mobile EEG headset) with metadata from a different source (e.g. GPS data from a smartphone) can further improve emotion measurement and help the researcher understand reasons for specific emotions.

Technologies can also facilitate the interpretation of emotion-related data. Data management software, such as iMotions (www.imotions.com), provide interfaces for different tools and lets the researcher combine and evaluate the data in one data hub. Although the presented technologies provide valuable opportunities to facilitate emotion research, the data interpretation through a human researcher remains

crucial. However, interpreting emotion-related data is complex and not an easy task. Many of the tools and technologies presented in this paper need lots of preparation, training of the researcher, and intense calibration of the data. These tasks are, however, not the focus of this paper.

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On the search for understanding car exterior designs' perception: A behavioral and psychophysiological approach

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Abstract In a very competitive automotive industry, new ways of innovation must be pursued. To understand consumers' reactions and to be able to innovate, one must understand how perception is held in a dynamic way and through the use of objective measures. Knowing that physiological and behavioral changes can reflect either emotional or attentional capture, the goal of this study was to evaluate whether car exterior designs could evoke significant reactions through the use of these dynamic and objective measures. Hence, different pictures of car exteriors were divided into two types: concept (C; non-commercialized cars, innovative designs), and non-concept (NC; commercialized cars), as studies have already shown that more innovative designs are cognitively more demanding (Carbon, Hutzler, & Minge, 2006). In a dot probe task, two cars were shown simultaneously for 500ms, followed by a dot, with participants having to push a button depending on which side the dot appeared on. Reaction time, electrodermal activity and eye movements were registered during the task. NC cars elicited higher mean electrodermal response and saccadic peak velocity than C cars. An exploratory analysis also revealed significant differences regarding different car shapes.

Keywords Attention, Emotion, Car design, Electrodermal activity, Eye movement

Introduction

The automotive industry is highly competitive, and to face this concurrence, car manufacturers must try to differentiate themselves from its competitors and elicit the interest of potential consumers. As technological development has evened the perceived differences among manufacturers in terms of quality and performance, it is extremely important for a manufacturer to find other type of solutions.

In order to find these new solutions, it is essential to understand what consumers want when using a product, as well as what are the different processes involved. They do no longer think about cars just for their sole function (i.e., transportation). Instead, they expect to fill needs, such as the pleasure of use or the matching of social values. In an ever-changing market, consumers want elements that stimulate their senses, and that are capable of being included into their lifestyles, allowing them to live an experience. They seek to be rewarded with psychological, symbolic, emotional and hedonic experiences (Schmitt, 2000). One solution may be to create more emotional products. To be able to do that, we have to study consumers' emotional reactions to products.

But what exactly constitutes an *emotion* when talking about an "emotional experience"? For Scherer (2000), an emotion is an episode with synchronized changes

of various components, including: cognitive processes, somato-visceral systems of adaptation and regulation, facial expressions, tendencies for action and subjective feelings. They are also evoked by stimuli with a particular significance for the individual (Fridja & Mesquita, 1994), and have a short duration (from seconds to some minutes; Ekman, 1992). Under a dimensional approach, emotions can be defined by two dimensions: *arousal* (referring to the activation level) and *valence* (positive, neutral or negative; Bensafi et al., 2002; Bradley & Lang, 2007). For instance, a picture can evoke a high arousal level and a positive (e.g., a photo of a skier in action) or negative valence (e.g., photo of a war scene).

Evaluation methods of emotion are classified by whether they measure physiological or bodily, expression or behavioral, or subjective responses (Bradley & Lang, 2007). Usually, in consumers and products' research, emotional responses are considered and measured as subjective responses. Therefore, for this study, we considered the use of physiological measures (see Boehner, DePaula, Dourish, & Sengers, 2007), allowing us to gain a dynamic perspective on the interactions with the product, without the consumer needing to verbalize or explain his sensations and reactions. Moreover, technological advances have made it possible to record these reactions in flexible, reliable, and non-invasive

ways.

These physiological measures reflect the autonomic nervous system (ANS) activity. This system is divided in two branches: the sympathetic system (that allows the organism to act, in order to be ready to react) and the parasympathetic system (that allows the organism to rest and recover its resources; Bradley, Miccoli, Escrig, & Lang, 2008). The most commonly measured indices are electrodermal and cardiovascular responses, with all ANS responses varying according to mainly reflecting sympathetic or parasympathetic activity or both (Mauss & Robinson, 2009). ANS activity is not exclusively related to emotional responding, as the ANS comprises a wide variety of functions related to digestion, homeostasis, effort, attention and others (Bernston & Cacioppo, 2000; Mauss & Robinson, 2009). Hence, it may not be clear when ANS activity reflects emotional or attentional processes, for instance.

Whether physiological responses have an emotional or attentional nature, their informational value is unquestionable. The way a car is perceived can influence consumers' behaviors, and, even though the global function of a car is unmistakable, the same cannot be necessarily considered regarding the elements that create a car (e.g.: doors, dashboard, handles, etc.). This notion can be explained by the central principle of Gestalt psychology, stating that "the whole is something else than the sum of its parts", "where each part points beyond itself and implies a larger whole" (Koffka, 1935, p. 176). Hence, if successfully achieved, decomposing the perceptual analysis of a car may allow us to understand some consumers' preferences and choices.

In the search of better understanding and measuring consumers' responses to car exterior designs, the goal of this study was to understand if it was possible to obtain and differentiate behavioral (i.e. reaction times and eye movements) and physiological (i.e. electrodermal activity) responses concerning car exterior designs. For this we defined two car types: *concept* (C; non-commercialized cars with innovative designs); and *non-concept* (NC; commercialized cars), presented in a dot probe task. Due to Carbon and colleagues' (2006) results showing that innovative interior car designs were more cognitively demanding and evoked more interest than more traditional interior car designs (through eye movements and pupillometry), and the innovative nature of the presented C cars, we expected to find significant behavioral and physiological responses at least regarding C cars.

Methodology

Participants

Thirty university students participated in this study: 15 female ($M_{age} = 21.87$, $SD = 2.92$), and 15 male ($M_{age} = 21.67$, $SD = 3.22$). All participants gave their consent, and they were paid for their participation. They all had normal or corrected-to-normal vision.

Figure 1. Experimental procedure used. Firstly, a fixation mark told participants where to focus their gaze. At the Cue, the car pictures were briefly presented, and the participant was expected to visually explore the screen freely. At the Target, the dot was presented, and the participant was expected to push a button depending on the side where it appeared. Finally, Recovery allowed the electrodermal activity to go back to baseline before the next trial began.

Materials

Tools

An Eyelink 1000 desktop was used to register eye movements, and an Affectiva Q sensor wristband was used to register electrodermal activity. Also, a questionnaire with a Likert scale (from 1, "I don't like it at all"; to 5, "I like it a lot") was given in order to assess participants' appreciation for each car exterior design.

Stimuli

Overall, 36 colorless pictures of car exteriors were used (18 C, and 18 NC). Regarding the computer task, the pictures of car exteriors were always presented two at a time. These pictures were presented at the *parafoveal vision*, which translates into a low visual acuity, being more sensible to emotional stimuli (i.e., it is the parafoveal vision that determines where our gaze will rest next).

Procedure

After giving their consent, participants started the experiment by performing a dot probe task, in which two cars were simultaneously shown during 500ms, followed by a dot. This dot randomly appeared at the same place as one of the car pictures previously shown, with participants having to push a button depending on which side of the screen the dot was presented (see procedure in Figure 1). EDA and eye movements calibrations were made only once per participant at the beginning of the computer task.

Participants were shown 18 pairs of C and NC pictures at the same time. After finishing the computer task, participants were asked to reply to a Likert-scale-questionnaire regarding their appreciation for each presented car exterior design presented. The side where each car exterior was presented, as well as where each dot appeared were counterbalanced.

Considered measures

In this study, we recorded reaction time, electrodermal response and eye movements.

Regarding reaction time, we expected participants to be faster to push the button when the dot appeared at the same side as the car exterior they were looking at.

Concerning electrodermal activity, it refers to continuous electric variations, changing from person to person, that arise when the skin receives innervating signals from the sympathetic ANS. Electrodermal activity can be separated into two types of phenomena: *tonic* (i.e., electrodermal level, referring to the person's global activation level, characterized by slow and stable changes) and *phasic* (i.e., electrodermal response; referring to fast and intense changes precise in time and stimulus-specific). As we wanted to measure participants' reactions towards different car exterior designs, we measured *electrodermal response* (EDR; phasic phenomena). A higher level of EDR would be associated with a stronger activation (*arousal*).

Regarding eye movements, considering the nature of our task and the duration of the pictures' presentation, we chose to analyze *saccadic peak velocity*. Also, this variable seems to be the most sensitive measurement regarding attentional state variations (see Di Stasi, Catena, Cañas, Macknik, & Martinez-Conde, 2013). Considering that saccadic velocity is related to the activation state in visual performances tasks (App & Debus, 1998), and that regarding data analysis, we only took into consideration the trials where the target (i.e., the dot) appeared on the same side as the wanted cue (i.e., the considered cue, C or NC), a bigger peak velocity was associated to a more important attentional shifting, translated into a stronger cognitive engagement.

Results and discussion

Our main goal was to understand if we could obtain physiological and behavioral differences regarding car exteriors. Globally, NC cars elicited higher saccadic peak velocity (showing a stronger cognitive engagement), and higher EDR (arousal), as well as higher ratings (measured by the Likert questionnaire) than C cars (see Table 1). Therefore, our results show that different car exterior designs evoke an attentional capture. Moreover, EDR results let us hypothesize that

the nature of these reactions may be emotional.

Theoretically, all NC cars were known to the participants prior to the experiment, whereas participants had never seen any of the presented C cars before. Therefore, these results may be explained by a familiarity effect being stronger than the "surprise" factor induced by innovative designs. These results go in line with Carbon and Leder's study (2005), that showed that a low attractiveness rating towards innovative designs could be improved with repeated exposure to those innovative designs. Moreover, Zajonc's (1968) exposure effect, where the mere repeated exposure (i.e., when the stimulus is accessible to the person's perception) to a stimulus enhances people's attitudes towards it, also helps to explain these results.

Considering a more exploratory analysis, car pairs were also organized by their shape. Categorization was made considering two parameters: *height* (low vs. high) and *outline* (angular vs. round). Results can be seen in Table 2.

We observed that low cars had higher ratings in the questionnaire, whereas high cars showed a higher saccadic peak velocity. In terms of low cars, NC cars were rated more pleasantly and evoked higher arousal compared to C cars, with the opposite pattern occurring between NC low and high cars. Regarding angular cars, NC cars showed a higher activation, as well as a higher saccadic peak velocity than round NC cars, with the last being better rated. Finally, round NC cars were better rated, but showed a significantly lower arousal compared to angular NC cars.

Even though a car exterior design is a concept too complex to just being divided by height and outline, we consider these to be promising results to further pursue and explore in future experiments.

In this study, we showed how it is possible to use physiological measurements (through electrodermal activity) and behavioral measurements (through eye movements) to differentiate consumers' perception regarding car exterior designs. Following the

Table 1. Significant results of C and NC comparison. (=): no differences; (<): lower.

	Objective Measures		Subjective Measure	
	RT	Saccadic Peak Velocity	EDR	Likert-Scale Appreciation
C vs. NC	=	<	<	<

Table 2. Significant results of exploratory analysis regarding car shape. (=): no differences; (<): lower, (>): higher.

	Objective Measures		Subjective Measure	
	RT	Saccadic Peak Velocity	EDR	Likert-Scale Appreciation
Low vs. High	=	<	=	>
Low C vs. Low NC	=	=	<	<
Angular C vs. Angular NC	=	<	<	<
Low NC vs. High NC	=	=	>	>
Round NC vs. Angular NC	=	=	<	>

exploratory results regarding car shape, further studies are being developed with the hope of shedding some light on this subject. The use of more physiological measurements is also encouraged, since it is the use of different indicators that will allow us to understand consumers' perceptions as well as to interpret their attentional or emotional nature.

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Symbolic meaning attribution as a means to design for happiness

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Abstract Material possessions with happiness-related symbolic meanings can provide a contribution to subjective well-being (happiness), because they remind owners of memories, achievements, or aspirations. Such possessions provide an anchor for personally meaningful narratives, help in the construction and communication of self-identity, represent personal values and achievements, etc. Capturing this richness in a design process is challenging, because meaning is person and context-dependent, and the effects on happiness are subjective. In order to provide inspiration for designers to create products predisposed to symbolic meaning attribution, six happiness-related symbolic meanings were identified. Based on those, 16 design directions were developed. To communicate the six symbolic meanings and the 16 design directions, a toolkit for designers was created, composed of a deck of cards and a website. This paper serves as an introduction to a workshop where the toolkit is applied, and it explains the process and the rationale behind the card set and website that make up the toolkit.

Keywords *Symbolic meaning, Positive design, Happiness, Design tool, Design workshop*

Introduction

In its classical definition, design is problem-driven. However, an emerging, more comprehensive understanding of design frames it as opportunity-driven: Positive Design aims to design for meaningful, valuable, and engaging experiences, without necessarily having a problem as a starting point (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013; Hassenzahl et al., 2013). Drawing from research on Positive Psychology, Positive Design focuses on individual well-being and on the opportunities for improvement towards positive states of feeling and being. It aims to have a long lasting and holistic impact that contributes to human flourishing. The Positive Design framework (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013) proposes that personal significance, virtue, and pleasure are fundamental ingredients to consider when designing for happiness, which offer different foci for the design. In particular, Positive Design focuses on enabling meaningful activities and experiences which support the fulfillment of personal goals and desires. Past research has indicated that engaging in certain activities can be an effective way to increase happiness (Lyubomirsky & Kurtz, 2008; Parks & Biswas-Diener, 2013), which can be supported by experience-enabling products (Desmet, 2011; Guevarra & Howell, 2015). We propose that the role of material goods in happiness can be extended to consider the symbolic meaning of products, arguing that the narratives they hold can also be a valid way to support happiness.

In this paper, we present the theoretical background that supports a workshop for designers in which a toolkit (deck of cards and website) will be used and discussed. Specifically, the SIM toolkit (“design with

symbolic meaning for user happiness”) is presented. In addition, the symbolic meaning framework and the design directions it supports, which are communicated in the toolkit, are explained. Finally, a workshop to apply the toolkit is described, and possibilities for future research are discussed.

The role of symbolic meaning in subjective well-being

Product meaning can be both concrete and symbolic (Friedmann & Lessig, 1986; Kleine & Kernan, 1988; Mugge, 2007). Products have certain functions, and specific affordances that allow users to categorize, use, and communicate about them. Product meaning, in this sense, is commonly understood and shared. Differently, the *symbolic* meaning of products stems from individual and cultural filters that give a connotation to products, their use, and their communication. The symbolic meaning we describe in this paper refers to personally significant abstractions (e.g., memories, achievements, aspirations). Such symbolic meanings give the associated products the quality of having notable worth and relevance for the owner.

Past research on happiness has proposed that, in general, material possessions have a limited impact on subjective well-being, because people have the tendency to adapt quickly to products, which may result in a hedonic treadmill effect (Ahuvia & Wong, 1995; Chancellor & Lyubomirsky, 2011). However, certain symbolically charged possessions defy these assumptions (Yang & Galak, 2015), especially when these possessions prolong and allow the re-consumption of certain experiences (e.g., souvenirs)

Figure 1. The cork of a wine bottle drunk by a couple on their first date, preserved in a three-dimensional frame. It represents a special moment in an intimate relationship.

(Love & Sheldon, 1998), represent and mediate relationships (Csikszentmihalyi & Rochberg-Halton, 1981), help build and communicate one's identity (Ledgerwood et al., 2007), or provide an anchor for personally meaningful narratives (e.g., heirlooms) (Jung et al., 2011). In order to understand in more detail how material possessions can have an impact on happiness, six happiness-related symbolic meanings were identified in material possessions (Casais, Mugge & Desmet, 2016). Based on Ryff's model of psychological well-being (Ryff, 1989), rich narrations of personally meaningful objects were analyzed based on their happiness-related symbolic meaning: 1) positive relations with others, 2) personal growth, 3) purpose in life, 4) environmental mastery, 5) autonomy, and 6) self-acceptance. While these six symbolic meanings are constructed through human interactions, life experiences, and thoughts, material possessions can play a role in their representation, encouragement, and recollection. Below, we will elucidate the six symbolic meanings and provide examples of material possessions for each. (While each example was described as being closely linked to one symbolic meaning, they are non-exclusive, being able to represent multiple happiness-related symbolic meanings.)

Personal, reciprocal relations with others can have a very direct impact on happiness for the emotional and physical support they provide (Lyubomirsky, 2008). Moreover, they contribute to a sense of belongingness, which is an important part of human development (Baumeister & Leary, 1995; Mellor et al., 2008). Material possessions can symbolize personal relations with others, for example, because they are given by the counterparts in the relationship as a gift (Komter & Vollebergh, 1997), because they were inherited as a family heirloom, or because they played a role in the relationship like marking an important moment (see Figure 1).

Figure 2. A set of military name tags that represents a difficult stage in a person's life, but also the acceptance of past experiences and the development into maturity.

Personal growth is a determinant of happiness that occurs when a person changes and matures from his/her experiences in life (Ryff, 1989). The effort to continuously develop, learn and improve from past and new experiences can be encouraged by material possessions, for the associations they evoke and the situations they afford. Specifically, material possessions can provide new experiences, a means for reflection on one's progression, help build a person's awareness of their maturity (see Figure 2), or they can support and represent the transition into new life stages.

Past research has pointed out that purpose in life is fundamental for happiness (Sheldon and Elliot, 1999; Seligman, 2011; Lyubomirsky, 2008). It contributes to a meaningful and worthy life, and to a sense of directedness (Ryff, 1989; Veenhoven, 2000; Baumeister & Vohs, 2002). Material possessions can represent in a tangible way important values that make life feel worthwhile, such as spirituality (see Figure 3), life achievements, and future aspirations.

Environmental mastery is the ability to create or adjust the surrounding environment to fit one's personal needs and values (Ryff, 1989). Material possessions can support this determinant of happiness and consequently gain this symbolic meaning. For example, material possessions can directly enable certain skills which contribute to a suitable environment for human flourishing (see Figure 4); or, for example, by facilitating and representing beneficial networks and partnerships.

The well-being determinant 'autonomy' regards having clear standards that resist external influence, and behavior that is regulated from within oneself (Ryff, 1989). Material possessions that support physical autonomy can promote a feeling of independence, and consequently, of psychological autonomy (see Figure

Figure 3. A figurine of baby Jesus, representing a religious belief, but also positive aspirations associated with it such as kindness, charity, and a sense of being part of something greater than the self.

Figure 4. A sewing machine that supported a "Do It Yourself" principle of living, allowing the development of skills that contribute to environmental mastery.

5). Furthermore, material possessions that allow the expression of one's 'authenticity', such as a personal diary, may reinforce internal standards, and support self-governance and self-reliance.

Finally, a compassionate acceptance of positive and negative aspects of one's self is an important criterion for happiness. The well-being determinant 'self-acceptance' can be symbolized in material possessions that help build and express one's identity (see Figure 6), and that help to see and understand the individual as being a sum of good and bad experiences, of positive and negative traits.

Designing with symbolic meaning: concrete design directions

Identifying the six happiness-related symbolic meanings provides a better understanding on how material possessions can contribute to happiness. Although this may already give inspiration for design, it only provides rather abstract insights. To provide more specific insights on how to design for these six categories of meaning, further research developed concrete design directions for direct use in the design process (see Casais, Mugge & Desmet, 2015). Specifically, individual sessions with designers and design researchers were conducted, focusing on

Figure 5. A blood measuring device which makes the owner feel capable of taking care of themselves, independent and autonomous.

Figure 6. A custom-made bass guitar that is used for self-expression and as a means to build one's identity throughout the years.

analyzing a selection of product examples that were considered potentially relevant for encouraging happiness. This analysis resulted in the uncovering and formulation of 16 distinct design directions (see Table 1). These 16 design directions resulted from several cycles of clustering and refining, which aimed for a manageable quantity, without losing complexity. In addition, it aimed for promising interventions that retained a generative quality, i.e., the ability to trigger ideas, rather than merely pointing them out. Lastly, it aimed for specificity, i.e., the ability to stimulate diverse ideas based on the context or user. Both aggregation levels (the categories and the design directions) are potentially useful to identify, communicate, and generate ideas about symbolic meaning – complementing each other and offering different levels of focus.

The SIM toolkit: design with symbolic meaning for user happiness

Providing designers with the six symbolic meanings and the 16 design directions in the form of lists can be considered insufficient to generate inspiration in a design process. In order to clearly communicate the six symbolic meanings and the 16 design directions to designers, a toolkit was developed composed of a deck of cards and a website (see Figure 7). The deck of cards aims to provide a dynamic and compact way to deal

with information, allowing the designer or teams of designers to manage, create hierarchies or pair up selected items. The website complements the card deck, offering the opportunity to dive deeper in the specific literature, and to have visual stimuli (product examples), which directly relate to the symbolic meaning and design directions. The website has the advantage of being able to be updated with new and diverse content and the latest research.

Specifically, the deck of cards contains two introductory cards that explain the research and provide summarized information about Positive Design (see Figure 8) and the research background; six symbolic meaning cards that explain the symbolic meanings and suggest certain design directions for each one; and sixteen design direction cards (see Figure 9) which contain on the backside eliciting questions to help the designer understand and relate the design directions to the user and the context of the design. In addition, the tool contains a website with product examples and relevant literature, linked to the cards via QR codes.

Workshop and other applications

A 90-minute workshop was prepared to accompany this paper, aiming to communicate the research and disseminate the SIM toolkit. Participants who join the

Table 1. Sixteen design directions to design for happiness with symbolic meaning.

Symbolic meaning	Design direction	Description
Positive relations with others	Support meaningful affiliations	by facilitating the practice of group/ community activities
	Embody characteristics of a group	by using unique characteristics of the groups the user belongs to (e.g. culture, profession)
Personal growth	Support active personal development	by providing a platform for active reflection on lessons learned and future expectations
	Embody personal growth	by focusing on adaptability to accommodate physical and psychological change
	Support acceptance and growth from past experiences	by providing a tangible representation of the passage of time
	Enhance memories	by offering a positive context or activity to reflect on memories of loved ones
Purpose in life	Encourage positive change	by providing an external trigger that suggests beneficial activities or behaviors
	Provide a sense of control	by allowing the user to manage personally significant goals, or to eliminate obstacles in their fulfillment
	Keep track of progress	by providing visual feedback on progress towards personally significant goals
Environmental mastery	Support multi-sensorial communication	by translating messages into a sensorial experience
	Provide a context for meaningful interaction	by making use of the context or limitations as an advantage
Autonomy	Destigmatize	by enhancing the aesthetic qualities of physically enabling products
	Design for mindfulness	by slowing down processes or disclosing mechanisms behind products to promote a mindful living
	Redirect the user's attention	by design an intervention that requires attention from the user to distract from negative situations
Self-acceptance	Allow shared transformation	by provide tools for user input at an aesthetic and/ or functional level
		by providing a tangible platform to wear, share or display personally significant ideas

Source: Casais, Mugge & Desmet, 2015.

Figure 7. Tool “Designing for happiness with symbolic meaning”: a) introductory cards; b) symbolic meaning cards; c) design direction cards; and d) website.

Figure 8. The introductory cards, which provide a summarized explanation about the research background and about the SIM website.

Figure 9. An example of a design direction card (here represented in real size of 5 x 8 cm).

workshop will be able to better understand Positive Design and the role of symbolic meaning in users' happiness. Using a hands-on format, the workshop asks for participants to share and discuss their ideas and to apply the newly acquired knowledge in design cases.

The workshop is structured in four parts: In part 1, the research and the toolkit are introduced, and the participants are asked to choose a symbolic meaning card, to link it to an object they own, and to share the stories. In part 2, groups are formed and allocated a category of object (e.g., clock, lamp) in the form of a picture, and asked to redesign the product to make it more predisposed for symbolic meaning attribution. The groups are instructed to select a symbolic meaning, and choose one of the proposed design directions. After answering the eliciting questions in the design direction card and brainstorming, participants are instructed to browse the product examples in the website for visual inspiration. Finally, the groups present their ideas. In part 3, a discussion is stimulated using discussion cards containing questions, such as "What the pros and cons of the toolkit?", "Are all the symbolic meanings inspiring?" In the last part, part 4, the facilitator wraps up the workshop, summarizing some of the outcomes of the design exercise and of the discussion.

This workshop format was thought to include all elements of the SIM toolkit in a structured and condensed way. In the real-world, the SIM toolkit was formulated to be used in the generative phase of the design process at companies and design agencies; however, it can also be applied for evaluation of concepts or to redesign existing products. The SIM toolkit was developed to inform and inspire designers to develop products open for symbolic meaning attribution, which can have a positive impact on users' happiness. It can be applied in different types of products, like connected IoT (Internet of Things) products; and at different scales, like community projects.

The SIM toolkit can also be used in other contexts, such as design education, to inform future designers about possibility-driven design. For example, it can be introduced in a design classroom in the form of a game or integrated in other interactive teaching techniques. Furthermore, the toolkit can be applied in user research, to understand better the link between happiness and material possessions.

Future research could test the toolkit in the actual practice of design agencies in order to provide valuable feedback on the toolkit, and the product concepts and prototypes resulting from it. Furthermore, more research is needed to explore its relevance for other types of design interventions, such as services or other intangible goods.

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Affordances of intimacy. An ecological approach to human-product interaction

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Abstract In this paper, I propose the possibility of adopting an ecological approach and the concept of affordance to analyze the phenomenon of human-product interaction as a whole, thus considering not only instrumental interactions, but also non-instrumental and non-physical ones (Desmet and Hekkert, 2007). I claim that the concept of affordance has been interpreted narrowly so far, while it could be applied, to some extent, also to the affective realm, and thus to understand not only relationships of physical proximity but also of psychological intimacy. The aim is to identify key factors in the establishment of intimate relationships, in order to understand how the experience of intimacy can be linked to product properties. The topic of intimate relationships with objects is relevant in the field of design especially because it favors the acceptance of objects and technologies at various levels of intimacy: from the domestic sphere to portable devices, wearable technologies, and prosthesis.

Keywords *Affordances, Intimacy, Human-product interaction, Ecological approach, Expressive qualities*

The concept of intimacy

That of intimacy is an intuitive concept used to describe many different things, like people (i.e. an intimate person may be a relative, a close friend or a partner), objects (i.e. things in close relation with our bodies, like clothes and other belongings), or places (e.g. our home). With the concept of intimacy we can refer both to physical proximity and to psychological closeness. Why do we use the same word for such different things? Is it just a metaphor or is there anything in common among these things? What are the characteristics that give rise to this kind experience?

In everyday language, for example, we use the adjective “intimate” to describe a place which is private, cozy, warm, familiar, and makes us feel relaxed and comfortable, but, if we had to design an intimate place, what characteristics should we focus on? What design factors are involved?

A concept similar to that of intimacy, which moreover constitutes a nearly synonymous, is that of warmth.

Several studies in social psychology (Williams and Bargh, 2008; IJzerman and Semin, 2010; Fiske, Cuddy and Glick, 2007) have shown similarities and connections among behavioral effects generated by physical warmth (the temperature of an object or of an environment) and those arising from the experience of psychological warmth (originated by characteristics like color, material, form, etc.).

Other insights from social psychology lead us to a definition of intimacy, that, despite developed with reference to interpersonal relationships, can be applied to study human-product interaction.

In social psychology, the concept of intimacy is closely linked to that of privacy, which refers to the mechanism of regulation of exchanges that take place between the self and the outside world, and thus can be defined as “a boundary control process” (Pedersen, 1997). Indeed, intimacy can be seen as a specific level of privacy (Westin, 1968; Pedersen, 1997), in which the most relevant boundary is not the one referring to the person’s self, but the one enclosing a small group. The members of this group reduce contact with outsiders while increasing interactions between them. They share private information and develop joint projects and goals, in a relationship of interdependence.

As a consequence, the main feature of an intimate relationship is the gradual shift in perspective from one of “me and you” to one of “us”. This determines the emergence of a new system with its own unique properties, based on the presence of interpersonal premises and expectations (Chelune, Robison and Kommor, 1984). Indeed, according to Chelune, Robison and Kommor, “intimacy is a relational property. It does not lie within a person or in a situation, but emerges out of their interaction. It is a characteristic of a system, which influences and is influenced by its components” (Chelune, Robison and Kommor, 1984, p. 25).

An ecological approach to intimate relationships

If intimacy is a relational property emerging out of interaction, it can be addressed through an ecological approach. This perspective, as described by Gibson (1979), is based on the principle of mutuality of animal and environment, according to which, the individual and the environment are not to be regarded as separate entities, but as parts of a whole system. Thus,

in order to understand how a certain animal lives, we have to consider its integration in its own ecological niche, which means to conceive the characteristics of the animal and that of its environment relationally. Building on this assumption, Gibson describes the ecological niche as a set of affordances, that are action possibilities emerging from the union between person-related and environment-related aspects that are structurally proportionate.

Given that the environment provides multiple affordances, what determines the type of interaction that will occur is the ubiquitous and continuous process of selection that an individual has to implement (Withagen, de Poel, Araújo and Pepping, 2012). The appraisal of the opportunities provided by the environment, which is fundamental to understand the link between the affordances as action possibilities and the actual actions, is also at the basis of the act of approaching. Indeed, according to Gibson, the distances we keep are important for maintaining our safety and also to “obtain beneficial encounters” (Gibson, 1979, p. 232), and, in order to comprehend the kind of distance that should be maintained, the individual must be able to distinguish a positive affordance from a negative one. Thus, relationships of proximity are based on the perception of positive affordances, which springs out from an appraisal of the relevance of an external resource in relation to the person’s concerns.

Another key principle of the theory of affordances, which is important to keep in mind, is that the perceiver should be considered as a whole, hence rejecting the dichotomy between body and mind and conceiving perception as “a psychosomatic act” (Gibson, 1979, p. 240). This principle leads us to understand that a positive affordance can be determined not only by the functional value of an object, but also by other object’s values. I claim that, as Overbeeke and Wensveen highlight, “if affordances are about meaning, they are not just about functional meaning; they do not only fit our perceptual-motor skills, but also our emotional and cognitive skills. Man as a whole should be respectfully embraced” (Overbeeke and Wensveen, 2003, pp. 93-94).

The establishment of an intimate relationship, on the basis of the functional value of an object, can be observed in the case of the interaction with tools. As Gibson claims, “when in use, a tool is a sort of extension of the hand, almost an attachment to it or a part of the user’s own body, and thus is no longer a part of the environment of the user” (Gibson, 1979, p. 41).

In a similar way, relationships of intimacy can be established through the union between expressive meanings and psychological capabilities. In a recent study on music perception, based on the ecological approach, Krueger claims that music is a structured sound-time phenomenon with an instrumental value: it affords movement through emotion regulation. Moreover, he states that in everyday life we perceive music “as a resource we can use to do different things, much the same way we perceive tools and technologies

as resources that help us accomplish different tasks”, and that “we potentially use music to become part of an integrated brain-body-music system” (Krueger, 2013 pp. 1-2).

In “The ecological approach to visual perception”, Gibson takes into account this kind of meanings addressing them as “subtle invariants”, and gives us a significant example describing the act of kissing someone: “to kiss someone, magnify the face-form, if the facial expression is amiable, so as almost to fill the field of view” (Gibson, 1979, p. 233). So we can think to the expressive structure of the face as the bearer of a meaning that corresponds to an action possibility (amiable expression = positive affordance = approach allowed).

Gibson clarifies this point claiming that “the value is clear on the face of it, as we say, and thus it has a physiognomic quality in the way that the emotions of a man appear on his face” (Gibson, 1979, p. 138). With Gibson’s reference to physiognomic qualities, the role of Gestalt psychology in the formulation of the theory of affordances becomes clear. Indeed a positive affordance has the same attractive value of the concepts of “demand character” and “invitation character” or “valence”, developed respectively by Koffka (1935) and Lewin (1935).

Finally, we must remember that, as shown by experimental studies of Michotte on causality (1950), and Heider e Simmel on interpersonal perception (1944), the recognition of physiognomic qualities does not happen only in the case of the interaction between people or between animals, but also in the observation of inanimate objects.

Design factors for intimate relationships

In a very similar vein, the above mentioned issues can be found in recent design studies on intimacy.

Bell et al. (2003), talking about ubiquitous computing, identify three possible forms of intimacy: “1. Intimacy as cognitive and emotional closeness with technology, where the technology (typically unidirectionally) may be aware of, and responsive to, our intentions, actions and feelings. Here our technologies know us intimately; we may or may not know them intimately. 2. Intimacy as physical closeness with technology, both on the body and/or within the body. 3. Intimacy through technology: technology that can express of our intentions, actions and feelings toward others” (Bell, Brooke, Churchill and Paulos, 2003, p. 2). Each case highlights different aspects to focus on, when designing artifacts. In the first case, the main issue is that of privacy, which may be violated in terms of personal informations, so boundaries protection (both virtual or material boundaries) should be under attention. In the second case, the main issue is that of technology acceptance in physical personal space, so designers should focus on sensitive characteristics like temperature, material, weight, interaction patterns, etc. In the latter case the object acts as a medium, through which people establish or maintain interpersonal relationships, so the design of the artifact should be focused on aesthetic appearance, or

on communication channels it enables and boundaries protection, if we refer to communication softwares that mediate intimacy.

Other aspects have been highlighted by experimental studies in Human Robot Interaction, that observed the rise of strong engagements between people and domestic robots, such as entertainment, nursing and service robots (Sung, Guo, Grinter and Christensen, 2007; Friedman, Kahn and Hagman, 2003; Marti, Pollini, Rullo and Shibata, 2005). Many of these works have found that people tend to ascribe human qualities to robots such as name, gender, ethnicity, personality, and even cognitive or emotional states, interpreting their behavior as if they were governed by rational choices and desires. The attribution of anthropomorphic or zoomorphic features may engage people and robots “in a humanlike interaction, which implies politeness, reciprocity and self-disclosure” (Scopelliti, Giuliani and Fornara, 2005), thus favoring intimate relationships. Considering the studies in experimental psychology previously observed, the recognition of these qualities in inanimate objects could be due to movement, behaviors and interaction patterns.

Conclusions

Through the theoretical contribution of social psychology, a definition of intimacy has been identified. This definition has been reframed through an ecological approach, in order to highlight the key factors characterizing intimate relationships, understood both as physical closeness and as psychological intimacy.

According to the ecological approach, on the one hand, relationships of physical closeness with objects can be established through functional affordances, on the other hand, relationships of psychological intimacy depend on other “subtle invariants” or expressive qualities. The process of appraisal and the concept of valence are fundamental in both physical and psychological intimacy. In this we can find a link with emotion theory.

Design studies in ubiquitous computing and human-robot interaction confirm these findings, and allow us to understand how some key factors, like boundaries and expressive qualities, can inform the design of artifacts.

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Empathic encounters – Co-designing possibilities for a good life

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Abstract This short paper presents a design competition case study in which the aim was to design concepts for maintaining a good life in small villages in northern Finland. The research aim was to find how two collaborating groups, namely students and the residents of the village, experienced empathy during the two-month co-design process. The initial findings show that different aspects of empathy are needed and emphasized during the different co-design phases. In the context of co-design, it makes sense to operate in an empathic way; for designer, though, it is also valuable to know when to focus on the building, support, or communication of empathy.

Keywords *Empathy, Empathic design, Co-design, Community*

Introduction

As designers, states Thackara (2006), we need to foster new relationships outside of our usual stomping grounds. This means that we have to learn new ways to collaborate and do projects, enhance the ability of all citizens to engage in a meaningful dialogue about their environment and context, and foster new relationships between the people who make things and the people who use them. The case presented in this short paper looks at how these goals of collaboration, engagement, and fostering relationships were met. One common denominator was the capacity to be compassionately empathic.

This short paper first discusses the role of empathy when designing with people from a theoretical perspective. Then, it introduces a case study carried out in northern Finland, where the elements of empathic design were studied from the viewpoint of participating residents and the students designing with them, where the design aim was to develop structures for a good life in small villages. Finally, the conclusions present various aspects of empathy that might be needed when grounding an entire co-design process on empathic values.

Designing with people – different aspects of being empathic

Over the past few decades, designers have developed elaborate skills for designing with people. Participatory design and co-design take up networked, global, and complex approaches that are popular worldwide in advocating the inclusion of users in the design process from beginning to end. Co-design here refers to any act of collective creativity shared by designers and people untrained in design working together in a design development process (Sanders and Stappers, 2008). We have to stop thinking of design as just the construction of products, services, and systems and start thinking about these as means for people to act, realize their desires, and satisfy their needs (Frascara, 2002). This requires from the designer a better understanding of people, of society, and of the ecosystem.

Researchers and designers working with communities and socially concerned issues need to be empathic, to engage in the design process empathetically. Empathic design draws on information about the user and his/her everyday life, and it includes inspiration for design and empathy, or 'a feel' for the user (Postma et al., 2009). Mere feeling is not enough, however; understanding of the situation is also needed.

Empathy allows designers to imagine themselves in the position of the user, and vice versa. Cipolla and Bartholo (2014) add that in addition to being empathic, a socially responsible designer needs the ability to work "where you are" and the skill to meet in dialogue the "others" in the same context. Wright and McCarthy (2008) state that empathy evolves in the context of ongoing relationships and communication, without which people have only their own, individual emotional responses upon which to base their experience and thus design contribution.

There are multiple tools and techniques to stimulate empathic encounters, such as empathy probes (Mattelmäki and Battarbee, 2002), empathy mapping (Gray et al., 2010, 65–66), narratives (McQuaid et al., 2003), and observation (Leonard and Rayport, 1997). Design empathy is needed when going from rational and practical issues to personal experiences and private contexts. To be empathic is to be interpretative, respectful, and mindful. Battarbee (2015) calls empathy an "out-of-ego-experience", which means two things: first letting go or stepping out of your own perspective, but then returning to it, influenced by the experience. In her opinion, this frame-shifting between feeling and thinking is key to the wise application of empathy in design. Kimbell (2013) sees a move away from thinking of empathy as an individual trait towards a collective capacity. In her opinion, the opportunity is to create a version of empathy that recognizes its potential to constitute new configurations of people and things. Battarbee (2015) describes empathy as a trick of the heart and mind. When we engage in empathy, it changes us. It alters how we feel, think, and act, and this can be used as a fuel for the design process.

Figure 1. Progression of the co-design process in the Autti village case.

Against this background, the present article defines empathy as the ability to be compassionate. This kind of empathy is a combination of understanding and feeling, of cognitive and affective empathy, expressed in action. Design anthropologist, Elizabeth Tunstall (2013) encourages designers to move from having empathy to building conditions of compassion among the participants in a project. Empathy as an ability to act compassionately also means the skill to be socially responsible and take into account local perspectives in the design process.

The Good Life in Villages competition

The Good Life in Villages design competition was part of the Arctic Design Week 2015, organized in Rovaniemi, Finland and funded by a Lappish hydropower company, Kemijoki Oy. The contest sought new ideas for developing a better quality of life for the ageing population in Lapland and in Arctic areas in general. The resulting service concepts were created applying the principles of open design. For the contest, four teams of university students from different fields, such as design, sociology, gerontology, IT, and education, were each assigned a village and asked to come up with a “des-ign” solution. This short paper looks at the Autti village project.

Life is peaceful in Autti, but changing. There are still grocery stores nearby, yet young people are moving away in search of higher education and work opportunities, leaving the village feeling a little bit empty. “We miss young people, it’s very quiet”, says one of the residents (Dowdy, 2015). The use of an empathic design approach in this case felt suitable. Empathy already existed in Autti between the villagers as the community feeling and the habit of helping others was mentioned multiple times. As students were visiting the village as outsiders, however, they needed to empathize with the lifestyle, habits, and surroundings of the villagers in order to design with them. It was believed that by employing a participatory co-design process, it would be possible to build active empathy between people who did not know one another before and who had only started working intensively together during the two months duration of the competition.

The data and methods used here include a student report of the case that was made after the competition and a theme interview that was made first with three students of the team and then with five active

residents who participated in every step of the design process. To talk about empathic issues, questions like “What do think of the co-operation during the competition?” and “How did you design a suitable solution?” were asked.

Experiences of empathy during the competition

Three co-design workshops were held at the Autti village in order to build connections between the student group and residents of the village. In addition, the students visited the village and a few residents attended some of the student meetings during the competition (Figure 1). Residents felt that this beginning was totally different from anything that they had experienced before. First, students wanted to talk with the residents about their daily life and thoughts. One of the residents said, “It was great that they did not present a fancy SWOT analysis or had presuppositions about what should be developed.” Students were able to focus on residents’ experiences. Residents felt that they were valuable as co-designers and described the approach being cozy and informal. For the designer this kind of approach sets a challenge in analyzing the results and finding the main design drivers.

A key element of these empathetic encounters was that students went to the village and spend their time with the residents. They knew that the atmosphere in the village could be sometimes quite negative and pessimistic because of the political atmosphere, which supports urbanization and centralism. The students felt that they could not build solutions for a good life alone, so they concentrated on the positive aspects by learning to give compliments and building procedures of encouragement with the residents. After some good laughs together, a realization that the villagers could actually make a difference in their surroundings emerged. Residents said that during the design process they started to see and understand how many things were actually happening in their village. This also engaged the students in the development. They felt that they got something for themselves, so they wanted to give something to Autti in return. As the residents were enthusiastic and more and more came to each workshop, the students started to believe that their work had a meaning and good results could be achieved.

Students felt that having workshops was a good way of building empathy (Figure 2). In the workshops, they

Figure 2. Students and residents working together in co-design workshops. (pictures by Kemijoki Oy, photographer Antti Raatikainen)

divided participating residents into smaller groups and thus created more intimate surroundings for discussions. In building empathy, students wanted to make sure that they used tools and methods that enabled the participation of everyone. For example, they had “peaceful moments” before discussions, so everyone could think about and write down their angle on a specific question or idea. Empathy was also evident in the students efforts at building a concept that could work for Autti’s residents. For example, they did not want to build a mobile application because of the low level of smart phone usage in the village.

Residents believed that by genuinely working together, they achieved better results, increased motivation to continue, and also wider acceptance for the concept. At the end of this process, the student group presented the results of their empathic encounters in a main seminar of the Arctic Design Week. This presentation and the final concept promoted the “grandma energy” of Autti, and the negative image of a slowly emptying and vanishing settlement of elderly people was transformed to a positive image of a powerful elderly people who run a vital village.

Solution built for local needs

During the collaboration, three different, new viewpoints of Autti and its services were produced. The “village of death” saw Autti as a respected and beautiful place for elderly people who usually want to stay at home as long as possible; the “culture church” brought up the possibilities of existing premises and their potential for residents and tourists; and the “authentic village,” the concept chosen for further development, focused on the authentic people and Lappish experience of Autti. The team portrayed the village as “a hidden treasure” and won the competition with a design concept that focused on getting passers-by to stop and experience the village. The short-term plan included a “treasure map” of Autti’s nature, culture, and leisure possibilities, in addition to the provision of some rental bicycles for summer and kick sleds for winter. The long-term plan included authentic “grandmother houses,” which tourists can visit and also stay in (for longer or shorter periods) with the residents.

Telling, listening to, and experiencing stories can be used as a way to build empathy, and the treasure map created a new story for the village. It tells in an easy-to-understand way what might be interesting in Autti and why people might want to stop there. This

concept was chosen as a winner of the competition for three reasons: it genuinely gives a voice to the villagers, it is perfectly doable, and it has potential for further development (Toimiva Kaupunki, 2015). In fact, since the competition, the residents of Autti village have been actively moving this concept towards realization. They have prototyped the map in a village market, they are collecting a list of interested people, and they are forming a storyline for the places to visit. Finally, although these stories can be uploaded to a smart phone by using QR codes in the map, villagers want them to be available only for people who come to visit Autti in person.

Conclusions

Based on this case study, it seems that designers need to be able look at empathy from different viewpoints during the co-design process. Here, the design process was seen as an iterative process for co-learning and building knowledge that would result in a suitable design solution for a village. At the beginning, when designers are moving in, the capacity to build empathy among the people participating is valuable. In the Autti case, empathy was developed through conversations, sharing, and listening. Design challenges were formulated by the participants together, not beforehand by consultant-like experts. Both parties in a co-design project need to be ready to share and discuss. The designer does not only need to be empathic, moreover, since empathic participants also want to understand where the designer is coming from.

During the development and evaluation of ideas, it is important to be able to sustain or continue the cycle of empathy. This requires positive relations among people and a certain commonality of events experienced by them. In the Autti case, the students were able to guide residents to valuable insights and new perspectives of their village. The residents saw their village in a new light and were surprised at how much was actually occurring in their small village. Thus, being empathic and mindful meant that students were able to develop design solutions that worked for the residents and in their surroundings.

At the end of the day, a (design) culture that embraces empathy is a culture of good listeners and storytellers that communicates both emotionally and analytically (Battarbee, 2015). In this case, with the conclusion of the co-design process, a new story for Autti was formed. The village was portrayed as a hidden gem of

Lapland waiting to be discovered. When designers are moving out, being empathic involves planning the implementation together and dividing the responsibilities. This involves knowing the limitations and skills of the participants and actual possibilities of their everyday life, and it is only possible if empathic encounters have succeeded in enabling an understanding of the participants' situation and values. Then, with the help of modern technology and social media tools, conversations and connections can last longer than the life span of the design project, as observed in the Autti case.

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Reverse human factors – Why we adapt to processes and objects that are counter-intuitive and detrimental to human health and comfort

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Abstract Human Factors in Industrial Design has primarily focused on the development of ergonomic and user-friendly products that are shaped to fit human behaviour and human dimensions. In contrast, this paper focuses on how human beings are impacted by using the products that humans have designed. It demonstrates how products with apparently poor and inadequate Human Factor qualities develop and change our behaviour. The paper shows that through this process and these changes, we develop new ideas and new ways of perceiving ourselves in concert with our interaction with the product (“Reverse Human Factors”). Iconic consumer electronics and a number of other products are studied from this perspective. The case studies of Reverse Human Factors point to certain generic traits that should be recognized as drivers of innovation.

Keywords *Human factor, Innovation, Consumer electronics*

Introduction

Henry Dreyfuss (1904–72) is considered the founding father of Human Factors in Industrial Design. His work focused on how we can shape the physical world to make life easier and more comfortable for human beings. Dreyfuss’ work can be seen in the context of the twentieth century social design movement which sought to liberate housewives by tailoring kitchen design to time and motion studies of household actions. This was a reaction against the constrictive styles of the late nineteenth century in architecture and design. Dreyfuss’ ideas played a central role in the development of a modern American design culture acknowledged throughout the world in the 1950s, 60s and 70s for the easy and comfortable use it allowed. However, Dreyfuss’ achievements were based on the premise that human behaviour and levels of comfort could be observed empirically and were of a given nature. In that sense, Dreyfuss and the design traditions based on his ideas focus little on how products also shape us. Conditions and design objects have changed significantly since the 1970s, yet Dreyfuss’ *oeuvre* still sets the standard both for how classic industrial design human factors are taught and how they are implemented in industrial design practice. This paper is an inquiry into how and why these Dreyfuss standards, are now being tacitly challenged by a parallel approach, in which discomfort, inconvenience and even health risks are accepted in design for everyday use: Reverse Human Factors.

Method

The analysis consists of three 3 case studies.

The first two case studies focus on consumer electronics. The canon of ‘Good Human Factor’ qualities derived from Dreyfuss is compared with observations made by user experience (UX) researchers in industry on how people use smartphones and remote controls. This information is combined with marketing statistics and sales statistics for smartphones vs. traditional phones and statistics for touch-based screens in general. Ergonomic and medical perspectives are also included, as well as the authors’ experience from discussions on practice at the R&D centre of a major consumer electronics manufacturer.

These findings are put into perspective in the third case study and by a survey among students of industrial design.

The third case study is literature-based in the field of behavioural studies. It proposes a generic setting for the idea of ‘reverse human factors’ and the general phenomenon of user ability to adapt to poor human factors in the Dreyfuss sense.

The student survey was produced during an educational challenge presented to students on an industrial design programme at a North American University. They were asked to make individual presentations on everyday objects that they like to use but that also provoke discomfort and frustration. This small exercise was carried out as a spot check of current ‘reverse human factor’ trends.

Figure 1. Examples of devices combining buttons with touch screen. Left: Bang & Olufsen: Beo6; right: Samsung: Ultra Touch phone.

Case 1: Combined remote controls – an interim stage

The following observations concern a remote control device that combines buttons with touch screen functions. It can be perceived as an interim design between the traditional button interface and the full launch of the new touch screen technology. The method in the UX analysis was to observe a wide range of users focusing on the following questions: *Which of the two different interfaces (touch vs. buttons) did the users prefer? What differences were seen in different age groups? and What other factors had an impact?*

Users did not perceive the combination of touch screen and buttons as an advantage. Shifting from one type of interface to another made the device less convenient. This interim solution, bridging between button and touch screen technology was not preferred. Users preferred to adapt to the poor ergonomics of the touch screen interface, because of the additional functions associated with smart phones and the ability to manage large amounts of content data.

Users across various age groups preferred the touch screen interface. With regard to 'other factors', affordability proved to be important for all users.

Devices combining buttons with touch screens were a temporary phenomenon used until consumers became fully 'educated' in using the touch screen interface. Although it might be thought of as combining the best of both worlds – the good human factor quality from the buttons and the widening of functions from the touch screen – having two parallel interfaces was not experienced as a good solution.

Figure 2. US smartphone use in 2015. Using the internet equals the traditional telephone call functions. Source: (Smith, 2015).

Case 2: Touch screens in smartphones and laptops

In Case 2, we compared the canon of 'Good Human Factor' qualities derived from Dreyfuss with observations of the use of the glass touch screen of the smartphone. We also looked at statistics on how people use the smartphone, sales statistics of smartphones vs. traditional phones, and statistics of touch-based screens in general.

Touching small, detailed areas on a glass plate does not live up to traditional good Human Factor qualities or ergonomic values. Buttons better match human ergonomics and match the dimensions and tangible aspect of the fingertips. The use of a glass plate touch interface significantly increases the chances of developing strain and arthritis in fingers and hands (Kim, 2012), (Franklin, 2012), (Esra, 2015).

However, the multiple new smartphone functions motivate the user to invest the hard work in adapting

The mobile market is converting to smartphones

Figure 3. The mobile phone market is converting to smartphones. Sales of “touch-based” smartphones are rising in all markets compared with “non-smart” phones (Arthur 2015).

to tapping on a glass plate. In general, it is the smartphone that “educates” most people to use a touch-based interface.

In contrast to the smartphone situation, users of laptops already have all the functionalities of the smartphone. Introducing touch screens on laptops would mean users losing good human factors without having the motivation of gaining new functions. This explains why the introduction of touch screens in the laptop realm has not developed as much as expected (Buxton, 2010).

Affordability is another strong impacting factor. Sales of “touch-based” smartphones in different size (Salil, 2015) are rising in all markets compared with “non

smart” phones (Figure 3). Most of the rising sales of displays are for smartphone-related products like tablets and other consumer electronics. One explanation for this is the synergy coming from the fact that when prices drop, sales rise, and when sales rise, prices drop. The price typically depends on the market volume of the specific display size. Another reason for the fall in prices is the fact that manufacturing button-based interfaces is more expensive because they involve mechanical solutions, unlike touch-based interfaces. The discussion in the laptop industry on whether it makes sense to turn away from keyboards should be viewed in this light. In terms of human factors and ergonomics, consumers might well lose out in this development.

Figure 4. Global shipment forecast for touch screen displays from 2012–16. Source: (Statista, 2015)..

Figure 5. In general, it is the smartphone that “educates” most people in using touch-based interfaces. Tapping a glass plate does not live up to traditional good Human Factors or ergonomics.

Case 3: The bicycle – rewarded by broadening of perspective

A US Toy Safety Commission study of 4–6-year-old children learning to ride bicycles inquired into how this skill relates to and affects the child’s development (Mace, 2008). The study confirmed that children develop their motor skills, balance, and understanding of the physical environment as they learn to use the bicycle. The children’s enhanced motor skills and balance also impact their other activities.

In relation to the development of the child’s self-confidence, it is significant that the child starts to understand the environment in a different way. When a child rides a bike, he/she literally sees the environment from a different perspective and develops a new understanding of distances.

From the perspective of this paper, the child’s ability to adapt to riding a bicycle derives from the motivation of broadening his/her perspective on the world. Learning to ride a bike is troublesome and involves moments of poor human factors, but children are willing to struggle to obtain the benefits of moving faster than running. It is a fact that no bike fits a child perfectly and cycling can be quite dangerous.

The US Toy Safety Commission study observed that as soon as a child had adapted to one bike, he/she preferred that specific one. This was not because it was the best from a human-factor perspective, but because that was the one to which he or she had adapted when learning to ride a bike. The reward for adapting to poor human factors (the broadening of perspective) had already been obtained and there was no motivation for adapting to new bicycles.

Student survey

Through student assignments on an Industrial Design course at a North American university, a picture was drawn of the scope of everyday objects that students like in spite of their experience of discomfort when using them. Medical and sports equipment was not part of the exercise, which focused solely on everyday articles. The students were also asked how their experience impacts on how they feel about these

Figure 6. The child adapts to the bike and learns how to ride it.

products. The choices of products/objects were individual and not coordinated among the students.

The survey was based on four courses with 20–45 participants in each. The three main groups of products (defined by the number of times students chose them for their individual reports) were:

1. Consumer electronics. Many examples similar to those mentioned above related to touch screen technology.
2. Fashion / Clothing. There were many examples of reverse human factors. High-heel shoes were often chosen by students as examples of poor human factors. For adults, these are connected with a learning curve that is, in principle, similar to that of the child learning to ride a bicycle. The motivation is to ‘feel in charge’ by adding to one’s height. Again, the perspective of the world is broadened as with the bike. (There is also a complex issue of cultural notions about beauty ideals involved, which makes it questionable whether high-heel shoes are ‘everyday objects’).
3. Websites: Students often mentioned specific website interfaces that were difficult to manage, but that had such interesting content that the students learned how to navigate. In many cases the driving factor was about finding products for an attractive price and saving money.

Often products with a lasting good experience started off being difficult to learn to use. The more people learned how to use the product, the more they started to appreciate it. This situation could be identified as one of Reverse Human Factors.

Conclusions

It is difficult but important to see what is just a small adaptation to the use of the product and what is actually the product ‘educating’ us to use it and helping us to develop new behaviour. The happiness and sense of achievement in experiencing access to

Figure 7. From the beginning of time, human beings have learned to adapt to poor human factors.

new functions and new perspectives on the world is the motivation for struggling to adjust to and learning to use products with 'poor' human factor quality.

Interim phenomena occur between old and new ways of using items. However, parallel or combined ways of using a product were not perceived as a convenience.

The Laptop PC example shows that users are not willing to adapt to poor human factors if no new perspective is achieved by this. However, more economical ways of producing an interface is a motivating factor for the manufacturing industry when they try out solutions with poor human-factor quality. More research is needed into the degree to which consumers are willing to adapt to poor human factors if the product is more affordable.

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Alleviating consumers' negative emotional responses to really new products: The potential of product metaphors

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Abstract Although adopting product innovations could be beneficial for consumers, consumers often show negative emotional responses to innovations. An important reason for these negative emotions is that consumers experience difficulty when learning about really new products (RNPs) because the knowledge required goes beyond consumers' stored knowledge and using RNPs is difficult to imagine. To alleviate consumers' negative emotional responses, this paper conceptually proposes that using product metaphors during designing RNPs could be a promising way to facilitate consumers' learning. Specifically, this paper explores the potential of applying product metaphors in the design of RNPs to facilitate consumer learning through functional and experiential analogies.

Keywords *Negative emotions, Product metaphors, Really new products*

Introduction

Adopting product innovations can be beneficial for consumers because product innovations can provide them with new and important benefits. Based on the innovativeness level of the novel elements, product innovations can be classified into incrementally new products (INPs) and really new products (RNPs) (Garcia & Calantone, 2002). INPs refer to product innovations that are based on current technology to provide incremental improvements of product performance. A new vacuum cleaner that provides more suction power can be considered an INP because it is based on incremental improvements of the current technology. RNPs adopt new technology that enables consumers to do things they could never do before. An example of a RNP is "SmartThings" of Samsung, which is a smart home system (see Figure 1). The smart home system contains a hub and multiple smart devices that are connected it. The smart devices collect various information of the home, such as energy consumption, the presence of family members, door locks, and entry movement. Through an app, people can access this information and make changes, allowing them to monitor and control their home from a distance, which is something they were not yet able to do.

Although RNPs provide significant benefits for consumers and can make their life more efficient and interesting, consumers often show negative emotional responses to them, such as anxiety and stress (Mick & Fournier, 1998). These negative emotional responses are mainly caused by consumers' difficulty related to learning what the product is and what it can offer (Wood & Moreau, 2006). For instance, when encountering "SmartThings", consumers may be uncertain of the benefits the various home monitoring

Figure 1. "SmartThings" of Samsung (<https://www.smarthings.com/>).

possibilities can provide and be worried about how to use the system at home. These negative emotions can hinder consumers' usage and adoption of RNPs. Thus far, prior research has concluded that emotional responses are important for the successful adoption of RNPs (Wood & Moreau, 2006). However, we lack an understanding of how designers can help to alleviate consumers' negative emotional responses to RNPs. This paper aims to explore the role of product design. More specifically, this paper conceptually proposes that using product metaphors during designing RNPs could be a promising way to alleviate consumers' negative emotional response to RNPs through facilitating consumers' learning.

Product metaphors

According to Lakoff and Johnson (1980), a metaphor is defined as "understanding and experiencing one kind of thing in terms of another" (p. 5). A metaphor relates two entities: target and source. Based on the shared similarities, the properties of a source are selected and assigned to a target, to express certain characteristics of the target. A specific kind of metaphors is the product metaphor, which is defined as product designs that "intentionally reference the physical properties of another entity for specific,

expressive purposes" (Hekkert & Cila, 2015, p.199). Product metaphors not only relate the product and the source conceptually in terms of certain meaning associations, but also translate these conceptual associations into tangible forms (Forceville, Hekkert, & Tan, 2006; Hekkert & Cila, 2015; Van Rompay, 2008). As product metaphors relate a source and a product both conceptually and physically, it has the potential to facilitate consumers' learning when product metaphors are used in RNPs. When encountering a product metaphor in a RNP, consumers interpret it through recognizing the physical resemblances between the RNP and the source, identifying the source, and relating the RNP and the source. Then, their knowledge of the source and its specific characteristics can help to understand the RNP through relating this RNP to the source conceptually. An example is the portable Bluetooth speaker "SSSSSpeaker" of the brand aiaa (see Figure 2) that can connect with a smartphone to play music outdoors. To highlight its function of portability, the metaphor of a foldable cup for tourists is involved, aiming to help consumers understand the benefit of the speaker.

Using product metaphors can be driven by different design intentions. First of all, designers can use product metaphors for experiential intentions to trigger rich and meaningful product experiences. Designers can also have pragmatic intentions by using product metaphors to provide clues for 1) identification and 2) use and product operation (Cila, Hekkert, & Visch, 2014b; Hekkert & Cila, 2015). As noticed by Hekkert and Cila (2015), the pragmatic intentions of using product metaphors is relevant for launching new products because product metaphors can assist consumers in identifying the product category to which the new product belongs and/or communicate how a product should be used. For example, to help consumers identify that e-book is used for reading, the design of an e-book resembles an actual book, which can help people transfer their knowledge of how to use a book to how to use an e-book. In this case, in order to help consumers learn the new functions of an e-book, the product metaphor of a book is selected due to its most salient quality: reading. In other words, when involving product metaphors in RNPs, it is important to consider the most salient quality of a source because it is easiest for consumers' retrieval and identification. While designing INPs, designers could select some non-salient quality of a source to create sophisticated and interesting product experience (Cila, Hekkert, & Visch, 2014a). We build on and extend these insights by exploring that the pragmatic potential of product metaphors goes beyond assisting in identification and operation. Specifically, we conceptually explore how product metaphors can help consumers to learn and understand the *unique and differentiating* benefits of RNPs (rather than its similarity with corresponding product categories as in identification). Uncovering the effects of product metaphors on consumer response to RNPs is important because it has the potential to facilitate consumers' learning and thereby alleviate negative emotional responses to RNPs. More importantly, as designers are responsible for selecting the sources and mapping them into tangible products

Figure 2. "SSSSSpeaker" of aiaa (<http://enjoy-aiaa.com/>).

(Hekkert & Cila, 2015), it is essential to equip designers with an understanding of these effects.

The potential of product metaphors in RNPs

To discuss the possible effects of product metaphors on consumers' learning of RNPs, we will focus on how product metaphors are associated with RNPs through functional and experiential analogies.

A metaphor relates two entities conceptually (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). When the source is a familiar concept and the target is an unfamiliar one, the metaphor can thus help to explain the unfamiliar target through relating it to the familiar source. This process of relating unfamiliar and familiar concepts is similar to analogical learning, which refers to knowledge transfer from the source to the target domain (Gregan Paxton & John, 1997). Prior research in the field of advertising has demonstrated that when describing a RNP with an analogy in an advertisement, consumers' comprehension of RNPs will increase because consumers will transfer important characteristics from the source to the target (Houssi, Morel, & Hultink, 2009). Correspondingly, we propose that a product metaphor can help in understanding RNPs. Specifically, when a product metaphor is used in a RNP, the conceptual association between the source and the RNP is built when consumers interpret the product metaphor. Thus, consumers' learning is facilitated through mapping and transferring the knowledge from the source domain to the RNP. It has been proposed that successful analogical learning starts from the identification of the source domain, which is the precondition for activating the knowledge in the source domain. More importantly, visible similarities between source and target can be helpful for consumers' identification (Forbus, Gentner, & Rattermann, 1993). As product metaphors include physical resemblances to express the conceptual associations, product metaphors are equipped with the visual cue for consumers to identify the source domain and further activate the relevant knowledge. Then, consumers can map and transfer the knowledge to learn about certain characteristics and benefits of the RNP, leading to enhanced comprehension of the RNP. For example, in the case of "SSSSSpeaker", the unique benefit is the portability. The product metaphor that is used to build a functional analogy and communicate this benefit is that of a foldable cup for tourists. In order to integrate this conceptual

Figure 3. Product metaphor from foldable cup to Bluetooth speaker.

association into physical product appearance, the shape and material of foldable cups are also used in the design of the speakers, as shown in Figure 3. Thus, when seeing the speaker, consumers will identify the physical similarities between the speaker and a foldable cup. Next, they are more likely to transfer the characteristic of foldability, and the consequent portability, from the cup to the speaker.

In addition to a functional analogy, it is possible to build an experiential analogy between a source and a target. With an experiential analogy, the knowledge base used for the comparison centers experiences (e.g., first kiss), rather than different products, such as in the 'SSSSSpeaker' example (Goode, Dahl, & Moreau, 2010). Consumers gain various experiences of events in daily life. The emotions that gleaned from consumers' daily experiences can be stored in their memory, which is called emotional knowledge. Similar to functional knowledge, emotional knowledge can also be activated, mapped and transferred to create expectations of how targets will be experienced (Comblain, D'Argembeau, & Van der Linden, 2005). In other words, experiential analogies can transfer emotional knowledge. Prior research demonstrated that providing an experiential analogy can improve consumers' preferences of the product described in the advertisement when the provided base experience is preferred (Goode et al., 2010). The inclusion of illustrating a past experience (e.g., "like hot tubbing after an intense day on the ski slopes") leads to the enhanced preference of the product because the

emotional knowledge related to the past experience is activated and transferred to the target product.

As consumers have no relevant experiences with RNPs, imagining how to use these products challenges them. It has been demonstrated that helping consumers to think of specific experiences in an advertisement (e.g., Picture yourself...) can ease this difficulty and lead to enhanced evaluations of RNPs (Zhao, Hoeffler, & Dahl, 2012). We propose that product metaphors in RNPs can also ease consumers' difficulty of imagining relevant usage activities, through building an experiential analogy between the source and the RNP. Specifically, when encountering RNPs with product metaphors, consumers are likely to transfer their past experiences with and the emotional knowledge of the source to the RNP. Through activating and mapping this knowledge, consumers can more easily imagine experiences relevant to using the RNP and how this would make them feel. In this way, the difficulty of imagining relevant usage situations of RNPs will reduce and consumers' learning of RNPs is facilitated. For instance, "Mother" (see Figure 4a) is a smart home system similar to "SmartThings" (see Figure 1). Different from "SmartThings", the product metaphor of a mother is used in the design of this smart home system. This product metaphor is likely to trigger experiences related to asking one's own mother for specific information regarding the home (e.g., location of devices, presence of people). Consumers can thus build the experiential analogy from their experiences with their own mother to the smart home system, as

Figure 4a. The smart home system: "Mother" (<https://sen.se/mother/>). Figure 4b. Experiential analogy from personal experiences to the usage experience of "Mother".

illustrated in Figure 4b. As a result, consumers can more easily imagine how they could use the product “Mother” at home. Consequently, the difficulty of imagining how to use RNPs could be reduced by involving product metaphors.

Discussion

When encountering RNPs, consumers often have negative emotional responses because they experience difficulty when learning about these products. Building on prior research on how designers use product metaphors (Cila et al., 2014b; Hekkert & Cila, 2015), this paper conceptually proposes and explores the potential of using product metaphors in RNPs to facilitate consumers’ learning through building functional and experiential analogies. To validate these proposed effects, we plan to conduct several empirical studies in the near future to examine the effects of product metaphors on consumers’ learning and consumers’ negative responses to RNPs.

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'Neglect-Me-Not' Shelf: Exploring the merger of behavior and movement-based interaction

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Abstract Some studies have investigated aesthetics of interaction and embodied experience combined with product expression, however, the feeling towards everyday objects, such as furniture, have been mostly unexplored by design researchers. In order to better grasp this domain, a case study of movement-based interaction and behavior of furniture is described. After a three-stage process (inspiration, ideation and implementation), an interactive shelf was developed. The 'Neglect-Me-Not' Shelf is a prototype of a shelf which desires human interaction. With the help of dynamic shapes and technology, it reaches richer experiences in users through the combination of behavior and movement-based interaction. As observed through a pilot evaluation, this combination allows the shelf to express feelings, evoking emotions such as surprise and joy in humans.

Keywords *Neglect-me-not shelf, Interactive furniture, Object behavior, Movement-based interaction, Dynamic shapes*

Introduction

"The world is inherently meaningful for us, i.e. we perceive the world in terms of what we can do with it, and by physically interacting with it we access this meaning and express the meaning." (Hummels et al, 2007).

As interactive products become closer in our everyday life, emotional interaction with physical world is strongly emphasized (Lee, 2006). The emphasis on emotional skills in both product and human-computer design is growing as well. On the same demand for new interactions, the market is becoming flooded with products which makes users overwhelmed with choices. An aspect that the market uses nowadays is product attachment which elicits emotion into people, making traditional product design change into designing contexts for experience (Wensveen, 2000). There are several factors to consider while designing aside from emotional interaction, such as function, behavior or brand (Chakrabanti, A. & Gupta, A., 2007). Another aspect to consider next to interaction is the design. The physical shape is critical in its market success – it attracts, communicates and adds value by increasing the value of it (Hsiao, K. A., & Chen, L. L., 2006). In this way emotional responses can incite customers to select a particular product from a row of similar products, and will therefore have a considerable influence on their purchase decisions (Chakrabanti, A. & Gupta, A., 2007). It is clear, that the demand of diversity in design is needed and that human-product attachment is one of possible channels. However, while product attachment is based on emotional interaction, which means evoking people's emotions from products or services, what if these same products or services could express emotions towards people?

The topic of this paper involves everyday objects such as furniture. As from the movement-based interaction definition, most furniture is tangible, so it requires actions such as holding, moving and operating functional parts but as explained by Hummels (Hummels et al, 2007), (cit) *"it is not in the tangibility of the interaction as in its richness"*. Some studies have investigated aesthetics of interaction (Hummels, 2001), embodied experience combined with product expression (Hekkert, 2006). In order to better grasp this domain, a case study of movement-based interaction, through dynamic shapes, and behavior of furniture will be presented. This way, furniture can not only address practical issues but also create a space for playfulness, offering users an enriched experience and new opportunities. The goal of this research is to understand the link between furniture behavior and human emotion, through movement-based interaction. To investigate this unexplored aspect, we selected to probe a living room shelf.

Method

To illustrate the process of the project, we will use three (Designkit.org, 2016) stages: *inspiration, ideation and implementation*.

Inspiration

In this stage it was central to understand and re-create (Simsarian, 2003). The first step was to share understandings from the field and the behavior a person expresses. We used the '*Plutchik Wheel of Emotion*' to map out experienced behaviors to feelings. The wheel of emotion is a model to describe the activation-evaluation-power space of emotion, where each emotional state is defined with an emotional intensity and emotional orientation (Wu et al, 2006). For example, the shelf would punch or

Figure 1. The “Neglect-me-NOT” shelf in a living room setting (left) and the sketch of the scene, picturing the cognition and movement-based interaction (right).

vibrate erratically when experiencing anger. The second step consisted of re-creating a scenario, in which a shelf would already possess a behavior. Each teammate selected a general emotion such as happy, angry, sad, etc. and acted out as a shelf and others had to observe and describe the actual situation. With this method we created a story for each scenario, and with additional research, we created the guidelines for the context we were designing for.

Ideation

In this phase was crucial to ideate shelf on the next level. As mentioned before, shape and interaction play an important role in the product properties itself. However, as mentioned by Hsiao and Chen (Hsiao, K. A., & Chen, L. L., 2006) what brings products to the next level is (cit.) “...the relationship between product shape and the affective responses...”. Since we discovered the behavior in the inspiration phase, in this stage we explored possible dynamic shapes that could enhance movement-based interaction. It all started with desktop and book research of modern furniture design, mood boards, sketching and lastly, fast and dirty prototyping with paper and MDF (medium-density fiberboard) in combination with electronics. The ideation phase ended up with a real-scale model (one and a half meter tall) which was used in the pilot evaluation.

Implementation (pilot evaluation)

The result of the first two stages is the interactive shelf, which is evaluated in the last stage. A preliminary evaluation was held with four participants, in order to evaluate if the combination of behavior and movement-based interaction could evoke an emotion. The shelf was placed in similar set-up as a home living room. Methods such as think aloud and semi-structured interview (Hanington, B., & Martin, B., 2012) were used in order to retrieve information from the participants. Additionally, using the ‘Plutchik Wheel of Emotion’, we asked participants to rate the main emotions faced during the interaction.

The “Neglect-me-NOT” shelf

The “Neglect-me-NOT” shelf (Figure 1) is a prototype of a shelf which wants to have interaction with people.

The shelf feels neglected and sad when people just place or take a book. However, due to its dynamic shapes i.e. separate triangles, it can offer movement when the person is near the shelf (in a range of 3 meters). This range is captured with several ultrasonic and infrared sensors. If the person is neglecting the shelf, the triangles initiate the forward and backwards movement, inviting the person to interact with it. If the sensors detect the interaction (in this case the hands of the person reaching for the shelf), the movement will stop. With this aspects, the shelf wants to express behaviors such as *welcoming* and *approachable* as an invitation to interaction, it wants to be joyful.

Implementation (pilot evaluation)

In the first part of the pilot evaluation, four participants were asked to think aloud while interacting with the shelf (Figure 2), in a set-up living room. From the think aloud method and semi-structured interview, the participants’ shared:

- “It reacts somehow to what I am doing... and it’s kind of suggesting right now << Oh hey you! You ha-ven’t seen my area, look at me>>”. (Participant 1, female, 24 years old, Denmark)
- “I am confused, I don’t know what to do! Should go for the cookie box or the book? Both shelves are moving out very fast”. (Participant 2, female, 24 years old, Denmark)
- “Ooh thank you shelf! I just wanted to take that, this is cool!” (Participant 3, male, 30 years old, Denmark)
- “The shelf is angry with me because I have been ignoring this object for too long?” (Participant 3, male, 30 years old, Denmark)
- “The shelf is reaching out for me. This would be so great for a reminder. You know, I am knitting this sweater for like 3 years now, this would be a great way to remind me to take the sweater to knit since I am forgetting it for too long.” (Participant 4, female, 40 years old, Denmark)

In the second part of the evaluation we asked participants to rate (Table 1) the main emotions they felt according to the Plutchik Wheel of Emotion: joy, trust, fear, surprise, sadness, disgust, anger,

Figure 2. The graph represents the raking of the 9 emotions, ranked by 4 participants in the implementation (pilot evaluation) phase.

anticipation. Surprise was the most rated emotion by 45%, followed by **Joy**, presenting 22% and lastly, **Anticipation, Interest and Fear** share 11% (Figure 2).

Discussion and conclusion

The shelf was chosen because, from personal observation, we tend to neglect it. Humans tend to minimize the interaction, especially when the only (inter)action is placing and taking objects from it. The shelf resulted as a great example, although this approach could be extended to more objects. The tangible world offers a lot of opportunities to explore, especially by adding behavior and movement-based interaction. We extend the call to the readers to explore different behaviors, shapes, interactions in order to create richer experiences.

At the beginning, when we designed the shelf, our goal was to make the shelf very welcoming, with the triangles going outwards and backwards very slowly, creating a pleasant environment. According to the Plutchik Wheel of Emotion, we were aiming at the emotion Joy (specifically serenity), however the most evoked emotion was Surprise, since participants did not expect the shelves to move towards them. In the interviews some thought that the shelf is angry, others experienced the feeling of invitation or even as reminder.

Our exploratory study consisted of three main phases: (a) Understanding emotions and acting out behaviors of shelves, which resulted in design guidelines. The observation made it clear that the overall emotion the shelves were feeling was anger towards humans that is why the concept of the “Neglect-me-not” shelf was

Table 1. Rank of 9 emotions according to the Plutchik Wheel of Emotion, ranked by 4 participants in the implementation (pilot evaluation) phase.

	Emotion 1	Emotion 2	Emotion 3
Participant 1	Surprise	Joy	-
Participant 2	Surprise	Fear	-
Participant 3	Surprise	Joy	-
Participant 4	Anticipation	Interest	Surprise

realized. Acting as a shelf helped us better grasp the context of the design. Especially, when a teammate would throw a book to the shelf (in this case a person), the shelf would throw the book back with same force. This made us realize that we can impersonate the shelves and give them human behavior, so people could better connect with them. (b) In the ideation phase, many shapes were explored such as linear on a wall set-up, rectangular, circular and free shapes. The triangular followed to be the most appropriate shape that would allow all real-size parts to move, in a living room setting. Moreover, the shape offered a clean movement and authentic furniture aesthetics. Lastly, (c) It is clear that the domain emotion people experience while interacting with the shelf is surprise.

With such project it is expected that bringing furniture to the next level doesn't mean only expressing behavior, but also changing human attitude towards it. As designers we then ask ourselves, what does it mean for the future of furniture?

Our initial assumption proves how the combination of dynamic shape and movement-based interaction add behavior in an everyday object, such as a shelf, and moreover, with such behavior, we can elicit emotion of surprise and joy in people.

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Loose parts for children with autism: Design opportunities and implications

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Abstract Loose parts are ambiguous and open-ended materials that provide endless possibilities in children's play. Loose parts foster creative and dramatic play which in turn stimulates the development of children's social, emotional and cognitive skills. In this paper we explore the potential value of loose parts for children with autism because their development of said skills tends to either not happen or at a very low pace. We describe the effects of a lagging Theory of Mind and Sensory Integration Disorder, which are both often associated with autistic spectrum disorders. This brings the diverse and complex nature of these disorders to light, virtually excluding universal design guidelines. However, several concrete design implications and opportunities are suggested. Our next steps entail engaging with autistic children in their context and trying out tailor made loose parts.

Keywords Autism, Design for play, Inclusive design, Child development, Sensory integration disorder

Introduction

Play is important for children's social, emotional, and cognitive development (Frost, Wortham, & Reifel, 2012). Of the many different types of play exhibited by children, 'dramatic play' is significantly beneficial due to its complex nature. By acting out long scenarios, whilst adopting many different roles, children develop a vast array of skills including language skills, speech skills, cooperative skills, problem solving skills and other advanced social skills (Sroka, 2006).

Dramatic play is particularly stimulated by so-called 'loose parts' (Daly & Beloglovsky, 2015; Nicholson, 1971). 'Loose parts' are movable objects and materials that are ambiguous to some extent, allowing children's creativity to determine its use or purpose. Examples of loose parts are pinecones, soup cans or car tires. They can also be purposely designed; for example large Styrofoam blocks (Maxwell, Mitchell, & Evans, 2008) or LEGO. A timeless example of a loose part that stimulates dramatic play is a simple large cardboard box.

The effects of loose parts on children and their play has been studied thoroughly, however most of the work is conducted on typically developing children (Sroka, 2006). Very little research has been done on how non-typically developing children play with loose parts. In this paper we focus on children with autism. The American Psychiatric Association states that the "essential features of Autistic Disorder are the presence of markedly abnormal or impaired development in social interaction and communication and a markedly restricted repertoire of activity and interests" (APA, 1994). The presence and severity of these features differ greatly between individuals. Aside from lacking communication and social skills, individuals with autism can also lack creativity (Sroka, 2006) and tend to show little to no

interest in activities that lie outside of their often sole preoccupation (for example, they can be fascinated with astrology, dinosaurs, trains or even batteries).

For children with autism the aforementioned skills tend to not develop or at a very low pace. Because these skills are implemented and honed during play their perception and implementation of play is inherently different, especially at younger ages. We see an opportunity for designing loose parts that stimulate the development of communication and social skills in children with autism.

This paper will first discuss the nature of autistic children in greater detail and the implications for designing loose parts for them. The paper will focus on two separate conditions that are often associated with autism and can account for most of the child's behavior: a lagging Theory of Mind and Sensory Integration Disorder.

Lagging of Theory of Mind

Theory of Mind (ToM) entails the grasp of the concept that every individual person has a mind of his or her own and that they perceive things in their own way. Having 'a developed ToM' means being able to 'put oneself in someone else's shoes', or being able to describe, understand and predict the emotions, intentions, motivations and perception of others (Korkmaz, 2011). Having an underdeveloped- or lagging of ToM can result in having a rather egocentric perspective on life.

The effects of a lagging Theory of Mind

Although normally developing children between the ages of 3-4 show signs of a developing ToM, a child with autism will either not show these signs or at a much later age (Korkmaz, 2011; Sroka, 2006). Figure 1 shows an example of the false-belief test, which

Figure 1. An example of a false belief test. The child answers incorrectly which, if the child is above the age of 4, indicates an underdeveloped Theory of Mind. The false answer comes from the fact that the child does not realize that 'Billy' will perceive the box of crayons in his own way and does not share the knowledge that the child himself has.

demonstrates the principle and is often used to evaluate a subject's ToM.

For children with autism a lagging ToM can hinder play in two main ways aside from the inevitable and obvious difficulty with social integration. These children have difficulty using 'actors' (like dolls) to facilitate dramatic play and engaging in 'make-believe'.

Being able to perceive the world through something other than one's own eyes is a prerequisite for (individual) dramatic play facilitated through props or toys. Pretending a doll represents a person during play, especially when imagining a conversation between two dolls, requires the child to perceive the world through the eyes of the actors (dolls). Because this process requires a developed ToM these children are less likely to use props like dolls as actors (Sroka, 2006).

A child with autism and a lagging ToM can have difficulty with make-believe for two reasons. The first of which is the same as the aforementioned reason for difficulty with actor substitution; having to adopt a role. The second important factor is that a large part of make-believe is using (ambiguous) objects to represent something other than what they actually are; like pretending a wooden block is a car. This requires the acceptance of the fact that objects can have multiple interpretations – accepting that the subject's interpretation might not be the only one – which is part of the ToM skillset (Lillard, 1993). An underdeveloped ToM can directly impede this ability to pretend.

Design implications for a lagging ToM

The two abovementioned effects (difficulty with actor substitution and difficulty with make-believe) associated with a lagging or underdeveloped ToM should be taken into account when designing loose parts for autistic children. The implications discussed below are summarized in Table 1.

The decreased ability to use props or toys as actors can be translated into a design requirement by stating that the loose part should not solely be interpretable as a separate entity (a toy animal) but instead they should be passive entities (like tools). Depending on the individual's ability, extensions of the user's entity are also possible (the user in a toy car).

The difficulty with make-believe can be taken into account by regulating the degree of ambiguity and finding the right balance. Making the loose part too

Table 1. The findings and recommendations related to a Lagging Theory of Mind (ToM).

Theory of Mind (ToM) related findings	Recommendation
Children with a lagging ToM have difficulty using actors during play, like dolls. They don't naturally bring the actor to life or pretend to be the actor.	Toys should not solely be interpretable as an entity that is not the user but instead by passive entities or possibly less abstract extensions of the user's entity.
Children with a lagging ToM have difficulty with make-believe. They have trouble letting go of a meaning once it has been attributed to an object and avoid objects if they can't attribute any meaning.	The ambiguity in the toys should be regulated. Too little and the toy misses the main value of a loose part but too much and a child won't know what to do with the toy.

ambiguous may result in that it does not resemble anything, and the child will not know 'how' to play with it and avoid interaction (Sroka, 2006). On the other hand making the loose part too directed is very limiting, because once a 'use' or 'meaning' has been attributed to a specific toy, the child will have difficulty letting go and will not naturally explore other possibilities, essentially missing the value of a 'loose part'.

Sensory Integration Disorder

Researchers speculate that individuals with autism might have differences in their sensory perception, which is further strengthened by the supposed neurological cause behind the disorder (Hebert, 2003). Difficulty with sensory perception is often described as Sensory Integration Disorder (SID) which, although it is an 'independent disorder', is often associated with autistic children. 'Sensory integration' is the process of obtaining, analyzing and reacting upon sensations from one's environment and own body.

The observable consequences of having SID are that children can get extremely over- or underwhelmed when exposed to seemingly trivial stimuli. These children can show hypersensitivity, hyposensitivity or both for the auditory, visual, tactile, olfactory (smell), gustatory (taste), vestibular (balance) and or proprioceptive (sense of self) senses (Hebert, 2003).

The effects of SID

Difficulty with SID can exhibit itself in many different severities. Most often children have a specific and seemingly arbitrary preference for- or dislike of- a certain sensation. For example a child can seriously dislike a certain type of food simply because of the way it 'squishes' or be fascinated by newspapers because of how they 'crackle'. Other cases can involve the child extremely overreacting (from an observer's perspective) or simply not reacting at all to certain stimuli. For example, a child can 'panic' when someone touches them whilst others have an extremely high pain threshold (Hebert, 2003).

The difficulty with the vestibular sense (sense of balance) can present itself in two different ways. A child with an under-aroused vestibular system can partake in extreme and repetitive moments of the hands, head or entire body to satiate their vestibular cravings (hand flapping, head rocking or suddenly sprinting). Since the vestibular system also regulates hand-eye coordination, difficulties coordinating one's body or hands (difficulty with writing or catching a

ball) can also present themselves. On the other hand, a child with vestibular hypersensitivity can simply dislike excessive movements (Hebert, 2003).

The proprioceptive sense regulates one's awareness of the relative position of one's own body and limbs (sense of self, also called the 'internal eye'). Corresponding difficulties exhibit themselves as general clumsiness but can also influence self-help tasks (like dressing oneself) or even cause oral-motor difficulties (during eating or speaking) (Hebert, 2003).

Design implications for SID

Due to the diverse nature of the difficulties associated with SID, any design of a loose part for autistic children with said difficulties should be tailor made to a certain extent since that which is enjoyable for one individual can most likely not be translated to the next. An overview of further recommendations is presented in Table 2.

Besides avoiding the unintentional overstimulation of a certain sense to which the child is hypersensitive, these discrepancies in sensory perception also provide opportunities. Hypersensitivity does not always lead to overstimulation; if the stimuli are kept subtle they remain manageable. By integrating a wide array of sensations into a series of loose parts a child can 'explore' these sensational variations in a controlled environment. For example, objects that offer different tactile qualities for the child to explore.

An under aroused vestibular system comes paired with a vestibular craving. An opportunity would be to allow a child to satiate this craving in a more meaningful, beneficial or less harmful manner than what they would normally resort to.

When dealing with children with a low proprioceptive sense their 'clumsiness' should be taken into account. These children have trouble estimating distances between themselves and others and when armed with large objects that they can pick up and swing around they can cause undesirable situations.

Conclusion

The complex and diverse nature of the disorders within the autistic spectrum makes it virtually impossible to create concrete and universal design implications for 'ideal' loose parts for autistic children. Associated conditions differ greatly in severity and nature, which implies that the loose parts should either be tailor-made or be adaptable to

Table 2. The findings and recommendations related to Sensory Integration Disorder.

Sensory Integration Disorder (SID) related findings	Recommendation
Children with SID can have an unpredictable but extreme like or dislike of certain sensations. They can be captivated but also repulsed by seemingly trivial experiences.	Taking a child's preference into account, toys should be tailor made or adaptable and avoid overstimulation. Exploration of variations of their preference can be immensely captivating.
Children with SID can have (vestibular) hyposensitivity. This sensory numbness can come paired with a consequent craving to experience this sense.	Using a toy to facilitate this sensory satiation in a controlled manner can allow the experience to be more meaningful, less harmful or even beneficial.
Children with SID can have a low proprioceptive sense making them generally clumsy.	Avoid the use of large objects that can be picked up and swung around.

individual needs. However, we believe that loose parts can be designed for autistic children and can in turn provide them with the developmental benefits that come with the consequent dramatic play.

For example, individuals with an autistic disorder can exhibit hypersensitivity to certain senses, which could cause loose parts to be unexpectedly utterly intolerable. This means that any sensory discrepancies must be taken into account beforehand and designs must be tailor made to suit the individual child.

Aside from that, children with a lagging ToM (e.g. autistic children) have a lower tolerance of ambiguity and less intrinsic motivation to 'explore'. This means that loose parts must be self-explanatory to a certain degree or they might be ignored.

Next steps

'Play' is an important part of an autistic child's development and the potential for loose parts begs for future research. Our next step is doing a design study with children and caregivers building on the insights presented here and guidelines by van Rijn (2012). First, we will gain a better 'creative understanding' by personally engaging with several patients and caregivers. Based on this understanding we will design and evaluate tailor made loose parts. This step will consist of i) video observations and ii) sessions with parents and therapists in which the loose parts and video material serve to evoke discussion and reflection (see Stappers 2014). We hope to gain insights on i) the *degree of ambiguity* that is both tolerable and inspiring for autistic children and ii) the potential *role* of loose parts in children's play (in both self-initiated play and therapeutic play) and iii) how these loose parts can ultimately contribute to a child's social and cognitive development.

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A smile between strangers: Enhancing social interaction in urban spaces

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Abstract As humans gravitate to urban centers in greater numbers, our daily reality is becoming increasingly marked by contact with strangers. There is evidence that engaging with strangers can have a positive effect on our mood; yet we tend to avoid each other, and feel alone in the crowd. What if there was a way to spark positivity among strangers in public spaces? This paper presents a design case to explore how technology can playfully disrupt daily flows by encouraging small but meaningful moments of mutual acknowledgment between strangers. We detail how two key design parameters - "connotative" and "peripheral" - were used to create a personal, body-worn prototype device intended to trigger interaction between people in public places and promote feelings of curiosity, connectedness, and happiness. We describe early findings of an original pilot study, and discuss possible future research directions and applications.

Keywords *Social interaction, Technology, Strangers, Urban, Happiness*

Introduction

Alone in the crowd

As life in congested, chaotic urban centers becomes the norm (WHO, 2016), more people are spending their days in places and amid people to whom they bear no discernible relationship. Faced with impersonal landscapes and the anonymity of crowds, it is tempting to fall back on the comfort of familiar communities, now conveniently portable within our smartphones. Anthropologist Amber Case (2015) comments that "the phone itself has more relation,

history and identity to you than an airport, for instance, or a highway. So you often find people using their phones in these kind of inhuman places in order to get back some of that humanity that's been put on pause." While reaching out to virtual stand-ins can give us a quick boost of connection, it also drains our attention away from physically present people and surroundings. In the long run, over-reliance on virtual communities may actually lead to a greater sense of alienation and loneliness: the anxious, paradoxical state that Sherry Turkle (2012) calls being "alone together".

Figure 1. In his "Public Isolation Project", San Francisco photographer Jeremy Brooks documented the many ways people isolate themselves in urban settings. (<https://www.flickr.com/photos/jeremybrooks/sets/72157625212318739/with/17673192096/>).

Figure 2. Facilitated interaction (center) can be a more accessible alternative to direct interaction (left) and ignoring each other (right).

The social potential of strangers

Modern cities have been ground zero for the “alone together” phenomenon even since before the digital era. In their portrayal of the social life of cities, writes Bearman (2005), early sociologists characterized urban social life as a sad series of “thin, episodic, instrumental, and univalent” interactions between relative strangers. Yet there is evidence that such encounters between strangers, then and now, may harbor untapped potential for generating happiness. Sandstrom (2014) found participants felt equally happy after interacting with people close to them as they did interacting with people they didn’t know well, while Epley and Schroeder (2014) found train and bus commuters who were asked to converse with a stranger reported a more positive experience commuting than those who kept to themselves, or who commuted as usual.

Despite these positive outcomes, our cultural norm against socializing with strangers (Goffman, 1967) has filled us with negative preconceptions of what such interactions might entail. To that end, we are not focusing on engaging strangers to talk to each other more often. Strangers are strangers, there are unwritten rules, consideration norms for each other, and we should respect them.

Goals

The research goal is to explore how responsive technology could be leveraged to enhance perceptions and overcome barriers to interaction between strangers. There is already evidence that the presence of an intermediary agent, such as a dog, can facilitate social interaction between humans (Figure 2). When crossing paths with a stranger accompanied by a dog, people are more likely to provide basic social acknowledgement (Messent, 1984), glance, smile, and start conversations (Mader, Hart & Bergin, 1989), and even agree to give money or go out on a date (Guéguen & Ciccotti, 2008). Strangers accompanied by dogs are also rated as more likeable (Rossbach & Wilson, 1992).

We explored more of that aspect by doing field research in different neighborhoods of San Francisco, observing and interviewing strangers that experienced some level of interaction triggered by the presence of a pet.

Based on these findings, we hypothesized that a responsive technology designed with the qualities of pet dogs on the street in mind - playful, engaging extensions of other humans - would trigger social interactions between strangers in many possible levels in positive ways. Like dogs, this technology would “nudge” strangers to look or smile at each other by acting as a safe, low-commitment precursor to the riskier, high-commitment interaction with a human. We also hypothesized that in some cases, such interactions would be accompanied by feelings of curiosity, connectedness, and happiness.

We hope to bring a fresh approach to new forms of social interactions where community-building has frayed. As real-world interactions become more and more laborious, we look into new forms of communication, beyond digital interfaces, without altering what it means to be human.

Design parameters

We explored a range of characteristics to define what constitutes an ideal social facilitator. These characteristics needed to comply with the constraints of a brief encounter between strangers in a public place, while maximizing the positive human impact.

Prior to our field research we named this social interaction as “Indirect Interaction” Inspired by indirect mutualism relations observed in nature, we named the person with a pet or a baby as “donor”, the pet or baby as “transmitter” and the strangers engaged as “recipient”. For the field research we observed and interviewed people in three different situations: waiting, recreation and transit. Within the sample size (n=10) of our interviews and sample size (n=25) observations, we found evidence of the indirect interactions. The most relevant findings for our research were:

- *People are willing to engage with a dog/baby regardless of the situation. Walking, waiting, commuting, etc. involve different social norms and the indirect interactions vary accordingly like amount of time spent or depth of interaction.*
- *Introversion is not a cause for non-interaction, people let their pets do the interaction for them. Safety concerns are the most common reason why people can be cautious about engaging in interactions with strangers.*

- *Privacy is not a concern, even with donors admitting having their characteristics expressed by the transmitter. Recipients don't seem to make any direct relation between the pet behavior the the owner's personality.*
- *The Transmitter's (babies's and dogs's) attitude definitely affects the response from recipients*

Partly following Ju and Leifer's (2008) model of "implicit interactions", which articulates the design of interactive systems filled with gestural aliveness, yet demanding less explicit input from users, and the urban observations we narrowed down to two design parameters:

1. Connotative
2. Peripheral

We define **Connotative** as the act of communicating in ways that are emotion-driven, abstract, and open to interpretation, rather than logic-driven, concrete, and specific. A playful and relatively ambiguous appearance can spark curiosity and project positive mood while leaving room for onlookers to draw their own, subjective interpretations.

We define **Peripheral** as a cognitive space where we are attuned to objects, but do not attend to specifically. Interactive objects with this quality can draw attention to themselves temporarily, but recede to the background when no longer needed. Strangers who are placed in close proximity to each other, for example in elevators and on public transportation, might appreciate the ability to easily opt in or out of the interaction.

The combination of these elements also mitigate against the technology monopolizing attention for itself, ensuring it acts instead as an enhancer of *humans'* natural talents for social meaning-making.

Figure 3. The device pictured off (left) and half-way on (right).

Prototype

Design

We designed our first exploratory prototype to be a standalone, physical object that could be embedded in everyday garments and accessories, such as scarves, hoods, and bags. Invisible when dormant, the device would glow brightly through the fabric when activated, triggering a sense of curiosity and cheer from passersby without placing undue demands on their attention (Figure 3).

In keeping with the design principles we laid out in the previous section, our prototype was designed to (1) visually **express** positivity in an intelligible but not overly specific way, and (2) to be noticeable in the **periphery** of people's perception. To satisfy (1), we chose the shape of a smiley face (two eyes and an upturned mouth surrounded by a circle). A universally recognized icon, we determined that the smiley face clearly communicated positivity without being overly abstract or overly literal or concrete (Figure 4). We solicited informal feedback on eight versions of the face, each with different arrangements and proportions of features (Figure 5), as well as options for color of the face when lit, and color of the cloth (black or white).

Figure 4.

Figure 5. Of the eight versions of the face, the version in the upper right-hand corner was chosen.

Figure 6. The device is invisible when dormant (left) A two-step trigger lights up outline and eyes (center), then the mouth (right).

To satisfy (2), we referred to Ju and Takayama's (2009) study of approachability and gesture and designed the prototype to light up incrementally, in a two-step process: first the outline and eyes of the smiley face would light up (signaling alertness), then the upturned mouth (signaling friendly recognition) (Figure 6). This instilled a more dynamic, lifelike quality to the interaction.

Execution

A shallow cylindrical case was constructed of plywood to house the LED lights, then outfitted with a circular cover laser-cut with the features of the smiley face (outline, eyes, mouth) for the LEDs to glow through. We used an Arduino to control the RGB LEDs. The LEDs were controlled by two soft buttons made of neoprene and conductive fabric: when pressed, the buttons bridged the electrical circuit, lighting the LEDs.

Pilot study

Method

As an exploratory pilot study, we employed a field experiment. We outfitted an experimenter with the prototype, a smiley face embedded in a white scarf that was invisible unless activated (lit up). We used a Wizard of Oz technique (Dahlback, 1993) to give the illusion that the prototype operated spontaneously; in reality, the experimenter was instructed to activate the prototype whenever he was in an immediate passerby's line of sight. Two other researchers walked behind the experimenter and noted the incidence of gazes and smiles directed at the experimenter. If a passerby clearly reacted to the prototype being activated, one of the researchers approached the passerby and solicited feedback.

The primary interests of the pilot study were to gather informal, qualitative feedback on (1) how people interact with the prototype and wearer, (2) how they interpret the behavior of the prototype, and (3) what feelings, if any, they had towards the wearer. This pilot

Figure 7. Front view (left), view with cover removed (center), rear view (right).

Figure 8. Two passersby gaze and smile at the prototype as we stroll down San Francisco's busy waterfront promenade.

was carried out in a selection of downtown San Francisco locations. We estimate that we observed about 200 people cross paths with the wearer, and got feedback from about 30 people.

Findings

Findings from our pilot research were preliminary but provocative. In terms of (1), we noted that the prototype attracted a moderate amount of attention. We were surprised by the relatively low incidence of smiling overall in response to the prototype. A few people waved, pointed the prototype out to their companions, gave us a thumbs up, or struck up conversations.

In terms of (2), passersby did not seem to attribute motivation to the prototype, or make inferences about how it worked. People were more likely to think it was

purely decorative and particular to specific sub-communities.

In terms of (3), few passersby reported impressions of the wearer: some didn't notice him, while others remarked on his physical features (young, male, Asian).

Based on the responses we noticed that most of the reactions were probably due to the unexpected ludic aspect of the prototype. Inspired by David Rose's (2014) theory of enchanted objects we hypothesize that by "enchanted" daily objects with technology using characteristics of fairy tales and science we may create the positive impression not just an unexpected playful device.

Figure 9. MUNI underground train station.

Figure 10. San Francisco Ferry Building.

Implications

We propose that thoughtfully designed technology can help facilitate such encounters, and hope our exploration of such technology will promote discussion around how to design for positive social encounters in modern cities.

To test the efficacy of variations in the prototype's physical design and interaction style, we plan to conduct follow-up studies with a more abstract design, and potentially introduce other sensorial inputs like sound. We are especially keen to deepen our understanding of how to design for "connotative" and "peripheral" qualities in a way that encourages people to be socially exploratory, while respecting their need for privacy and peace of mind. Future iterations may build in "intelligence"; however, limited intelligence based on animal cognition or some other limited capacity to serve as a catalyst for humans to be social and creative, drawing their own conclusions and crafting their own stories.

Possible applications include "enchanted" daily garments and accessories (e.g., bags, bottles, clothes, jewelry), architecture and urban design, mobility spaces (e.g., subways, bus stops, sidewalks), and transportation (e.g., bicycles, cars, skateboards).

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Sensibility in between: A phenomenology-inspired design proposition

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Abstract ‘Meaning’ is often considered to be held in a person (bodily and thinking capabilities) or in the qualities of artefacts (product characteristics). In contrast, within this paper, I propose to design for the emergence of meaning not only in the interaction but also in-between its participants. Anchored in the theories of the phenomenology of perception and ecological psychology this paper presents the Sensible Illumination concept, a lighting system for the home and work environment, functioning as a physical hypothesis to further both theoretical and design practical insights of the proposed interaction paradigm.

Keywords *Phenomenology-inspired design, Continuous Interaction, Engagement, Interaction design, Context-aware design*

Introduction

James Jerome Gibson (1986) has influenced interaction design over the past decades. Mostly with his work on *affordance*. Donald Norman popularized this concept through his book “The Psychology of Everyday Things” (Norman, 1988) which was later entitled “The Design of Everyday Things”. Norman uses the example of a door handle to elaborate that what we perceive is the opportunity to grasp (*affordance*) given by that our hands can grab (*effectivities*). Gibson emphasizes that the world is perceived as intrinsically meaningful as we are attuned to the world through our capabilities to perceive and act (Gibson, 1986). This emphasis on the lived body and its *effectivities* suggests that people perceive the world differently (i.e., for a child a chair is not sit-able but climbable).

While Gibson developed his ecological psychology, similar ideas emerged in philosophy. It was through Paul Dourish’s (2001) introduction of Maurice Merleau-Ponty’s “Phenomenology of Perception” (Merleau-Ponty, 1962) in “Where the Action Is: Foundations of Embodied Interaction” that the interaction design field got acquainted with this perspective that centralizes the experiencing body in the world.

According to Merleau-Ponty, people adjust themselves through skillful coping (Dreyfus, 2002) to what a situation requires. He speaks of the body’s quest for a *maximum grip*, a match of how the body can optimally deal with its environment. To him, meaning emerges *in* interaction with an attuning body while engaging with the world highlighting their (body and world) intertwining character. It is by acknowledging a subjective embodied character of our engagement with the ever-changing world that *contextuality* is of dynamic, intertwined and holistic nature (Dourish, 2004). Moreover, both ecological psychology and phenomenology stress the unity (reciprocity) between human beings and their environment, placing the interacting body central in existence and as primary means of experiencing the world (primacy of action).

Figure 1. The Sensible Illumination consisting of a series of light bulbs, and people. Both people and bulbs have action-perception loops to engage with the world. Where the directed intentionality meets, i.e., where a bulb wants to shed light and a person desires light, about-content light can be engaged with. Through engagement, meaning can emerge in-between.

Furthermore, Gibson’s resonance model, elaborated by Michaels and Carello (1981) in the form of a radio analogy, suggests that perception concerns the *tuning* of our body (as our perceptual system) to information, contrary to mentally capturing and storing information. We do so in holistic (*detection* not calculation) and continuous (in action no reflection) ways attuning to what is useful information. His theory of perceiving is a theory of knowing the environment. In other words, perceptions and actions themselves concern knowing, rather than having knowledge.

Design proposition

For design, this means that functionality reveals itself through interaction and builds upon the match between our human capabilities and those of the products at stake. The challenge is thus to design for human capabilities (Overbeeke, 2007) mapping its *continuous* qualities of being-in-the-world (*action-possibilities*) to the discrete power embodied in computing (*functionalities*) in a meaningful manner. Following that meaning emerges *in* the interaction between person and environment, *in-between* knowing systems; subsequently, we need to focus

designing on the *about-content* (i.e., dynamic match or meaning in between the body and the world) that brings about the meaning.

Design exploration

A lighting system for a home environment has been chosen as context for exploring the in-between-ness as inspiration for interaction design. The system concept, called Sensible Illumination, extends ordinary lighting with active and dynamic capabilities. Through framing the *action-possibilities* of the person and the *action-possibilities* incorporated in the behavior of the lighting: meaning is to emerge *in* the interaction and *in between* the lamps and persons. In other words, one continually engages with the light in context, not with the light bulb *per se*.

Interaction design and technical implementation

The interaction design of the Sensible Illumination is based on the idea to provide a person with light where it is needed or desired. The people carry a token that estimates this desire and signals this into the environment, which in its turn is receptive to this 'information.' This would be the lighting that thus perceives desires from people, which are as most lamps are capable of lighting up space. In terms of mapping people to the system, the *about-content* is light (which people desire and lamps can provide).

The underlying assumption that people desire light in front of them, in their field of gaze, was taken. And, that this desire is higher when the person is active contrary to inactive in which no light would be needed.

The lamps are *attuned* to *detect* the desire of people *continuously* while people direct their bodies to them. This desire is grounded in activity and whether the desire for light has been met already (i.e., environment light is involved in the interaction-loop).

Regarding the *about-content*, how the fields of people and lamps intersect: the *action-possibilities* of a person are in movement and directedness within and the *functionalities* of the lighting system are to merely intensify or dim light. It is designed for *about-content* to emerge at this intersection of person and environment/system: sensibly illuminating the active gaze of a person.

The Sensible Illumination prototype is built with Philips HUE lighting bulbs. Each bulb is sensible to the 'desire of light' in front of itself. Each person, in turn, is carrying a token that broadcasts the 'desire for light' in a forward direction. The higher the desire, the more light it demands. Within the prototype, the control of light is limited brightness and hue (warm – cold light). The Philips HUE lights that are usually discretely controlled are now updated at a rate of twenty times per second for a continuous interaction-loop to create light motion that feels direct and continuous, and thus to come forth to the continuous nature of perception.

Reflections

As part of the Concept-Driven Interaction Design Research approach (Stolterman & Wiberg, 2010) in which I aim to challenge and further the phenomenology and ecological psychology- inspired interaction design theory (Hummels & Lévy, 2013; Stienstra, 2015; Stienstra, 2016) and corresponding implications for design practice, the system was built for exploration and getting a grip on its sensitivities. The following situations that underline the characteristics of the proposed design paradigm occurred while interacting with the system in qualitative user confrontations:

The light intensifies when space is entered and dims when it is left again. Since the lights respond to the desired directedness, the lighting does not follow but goes ahead of the person. Turning, however, thus actuates several light bulbs over time and this makes the light move in front of the person. The Sensible Illumination thus enlightens the space of gaze which was experienced as "the light is part of me, it extends me". This suggests that the design enables immersion or engagement with the light. Nonetheless, it has to be noted that sensibility is required. That is, the continuity of light moving is appreciated. However, when light movement is mapped too direct, it is quite an evasive situation. Despite that the brightness and hue of lamps transition continuously over time, the 'switch' between covered enlighten areas is still discrete creating somewhat abrupt and disturbing transitions.

In case the gaze is already brightened by sunlight, the desire to intensify is not broadcasted and thus not picked up. When the desire increases, because of a sunset, the lamp continuously intensifies till the desire has been fulfilled. While the user becomes inactive, the spotlight fades out. Being active again re-activates the light in the space of gaze.

When two people meet in the same space, the light, as well as both people, starts to interplay. When both people turn to the same spot the spot illuminates. What is evident is that the people adjust their behavior in interaction to cope and control the light. It is a challenge to provide the light with a transforming behavior character as well to come forth to the dynamics of *contextuality* in people's behavior. The presupposed take on and use of people's desire to have light in front of them turned out to be useful. Nonetheless, the use of *desire* as a particular derivative of someone's *intentionality* requires caution, careful consideration and further validation in context.

Concluding remarks

The initial design explorations with the build system highlight a few characteristics of the theory and design practicality. The preliminary results from our qualitative user confrontations indicate that the idea to design for *in between about-content* upholds the potential to have meaning emerge mutually, i.e., emergent in interaction between person and system. The design exploration persuaded for engagement, yet at times, it occurred in an invasive manner. Paramount

to its functioning is *sensibility in continuity* that captures the person and light bulbs in a shared loop of engagement. The research will be furthered by gathering and systematically analyzing user impressions as well as behavior patterns that emerge. The phenomenology-informed ideas that meaning emerges in interaction and that engagement has a reciprocal character reveals that design could focus on emergent in-between meanings, rather than focusing the design on either the artefacts characteristics or user's experience. To design for an in-between meaning to emerge, it seems fruitful to focus on the continuous nature of perception and action to engage people and system with the *about-content* that lives in between.

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Auto-cam – An innovative approach to visual research for design

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Abstract The Auto-Cam investigates how design researchers can take advantage of photography as a visual research method through the design and deployment of a wearable 'POV' (Point-Of-View) camera. Photographs have a unique ability to capture and express personal perspective and promote empathy among researchers and participants (Van Gestel, 2015), but photography remains relatively overlooked as a research method, in particular for design research. The Auto-Cam provides a first-person look into someone's daily life and activities, using coloured stickers as a way to 'tag' objects of interest in one's environment; the Auto-Cam is designed to automatically capture an image when it 'sees' a sticker. We present the Auto-Cam as a case study showing the value of automated first-person photography and the importance of continuing to explore the potential of photography as a valuable research method for design.

Keywords Visual research, Design research, Photography, Wearable cameras, Empathy

PHOTOGRAPHY IN DESIGN RESEARCH

Figure 1. It's perhaps no surprise that photography is particularly well-suited as a visual research method – photographs can provide deep qualitative insight, serve as artistic or design inspiration, and be revisited for ongoing reflection. Photography has traction as a visual research method across the social sciences, but there is still relatively little critical inquiry into how we can capture and analyse photographs as design researchers. More recently discourse around visual research within design has grown; for example, questioning how photography can be used within HCI design in particular (Bariola and Faste, 2012). For example, snapshots like the three above taken during fieldwork for design research are valuable research material, able to inspire design informed by observed experiences. How could this woman's experience of boarding a train be more seamless, more dignified? How could we design a service for handicapped passengers that doesn't disrupt the flow of passenger traffic?

A POV CAMERA

Figure 2. While snapshots like those in Fig. 1 are indeed valuable for design research, they lack a certain intimacy or personal perspective that photography can be used to express effectively. As Van Gestel (2015) writes, photographs have a unique capability to build empathy between researcher(s) and participant(s), a quality vitally relevant and valuable for design research. We set out to explore alternatives to how we can take photographs for design research; in particular, how can photographs immerse us in another's experience? Enable us to step into the shoes of someone else? We looked at the visual quality of photographs and became particularly interested in photographs taken from one's point of view, as in the ones above. How did this particular person experience a trip to the supermarket? As we became interested in wearable cameras that allow for 'POV' capture, we also became interested in the potential of automating image capture.

Figure 3. We mapped out where photography currently sits as a research method, for example within anthropology (Collier and Collier, 1986) and user research (Rohrer, 2014), and again were struck by photography's ability to capture and communicate a person's individual perspective. In a UX research lab for example, photographs can capture someone's interactions or experiences with a device, but they lack contextual information, perspective, and real-world environment; we wanted to design something to explore that space.

Figure 4. We imagined the 'Auto-Cam' as a wearable device that takes point-of-view photos, automated to some extent. We mapped the larger context surrounding this Auto-Cam; how are wearable cameras already being used? For example, the SenseCam (Microsoft Research, 2013) was designed and deployed as a wearable, automatic point-of-view camera. We set out to differentiate the Auto-Cam by designing and using it primarily as a design research tool, building a framework around the device of how visual research into people's lives can be beneficial design.

DESIGN PROPOSALS

Figure 5. We brought together design proposals for the Auto-Cam in the form of a design workbook (Gaver, 2011). Above are selected images from three proposals. 'Loved Objects' looks at how the Auto-Cam could be used to capture a photo whenever you are near your most loved possessions, as the way you behave and feel around your favourite objects can reveal a lot about your desires, preferences, and practices. 'Social Situations' looks at how the Auto-Cam could be used to investigate our interaction(s) with, and around, the multiple devices that surround us, taking a photo every time a smartphone (or other device) is present, capturing the visual, physical context and interactions around the device(s). 'Multi-Device' explores how the Auto-Cam can capture our interactions with a growing, complex ecosystem of personal devices, both digital and analogue. These three proposals are all concerned with capturing contextual information about particular objects in one's environment, and we set out to design an Auto-Cam that could do just that.

MAKING AND PROTOTYPING

Figure 6. We tried out different devices, components, and programs along the way to make a functioning, deployable prototype. We began using the Arduino-based 'Ardu-Cam' but in the end moved to using an Arduino with two 'Pixy' cameras (one to track colour and one to capture images). This allowed the Auto-Cam to take a photo whenever it recognized certain pre-defined color combinations. We also experimented with including different sensors into the device that could trigger a photograph, such as a flex sensor (pictured above) and a heart rate sensor.

COLOUR TRACKING

Figure 7. As the Auto-Cam could track and 'look for' certain color combinations, we used printed coloured stickers as a way to mark or 'tag' objects of interest in someone's environment. When the Auto-Cam 'sees' a sticker combining an appropriate mix of two colours, a photograph is snapped. The participant gets to decide along with the researcher where to put the stickers, making the process participatory and collaborative.

THE AUTO-CAM

Figure 8. The Auto-Cam kit we used for deployment includes the Auto-Cam itself (in black acrylic casing, seen above), an information pamphlet, a consent/release form, and stickers of varying sizes and color combinations to 'tag' objects with.

Figure 9. The camera is worn in a provided harness as shown above, allowing for photographs from a first-person perspective.

DEPLOYMENT PROCESS

IDENTIFY

RESEARCH
TOPIC

USER
GROUP

TAILOR

KIT TO
TOPIC & GROUP

HAND-OFF

INSTRUCT
USERS

DEPLOY
PERIOD

USE

REVIEW
IMAGES

RETURN

RESEARCHERS
RECEIVE KIT

REVIEW

ANALYSE
IMAGES

INTERVIEW

DISCUSS

INCORPORATE

INTO
FINDING(S)

Figure 10. Deploying the Auto-Cam gave us the chance to test out our prototype with a group of 6 participants. We gave each participant the Auto-Cam kit, and worked together to decide which objects to tag with stickers. For example, what are their favourite objects? What do they use most frequently throughout the day, for work or leisure? Several participants jumped to tag their smartphone, among other objects.

COLOUR STICKERS

Figure 11. Participants placed coloured stickers on all sorts of objects, both digital and analogue, dirty and clean, loved and ignored...

COLLECTING VISUAL DATA

Figure 12. Participants were given the chance to review (and delete) images before returning the Auto-Cam. After this, we were able to review the returns, such as the images pictured above. We faced several questions: how to go about analysing these images? How to review and organize the visual material in a way that highlights moments of experiences of interest to us as design researchers?

VISUAL ANALYSIS

Figure 13. We experimented with different methods of visual analysis (Knoblauch et. al., 2008), including using the 'AEIOU' framework (Robinson, 2015). For example, in the above diagram we analysed images from Jason, looking at the activities he participated in (e.g. watching television, drawing, walking in the rain, and cooking). Without viewing the images chronologically we can see that Jason spent a large portion of this time drawing, so we flagged his workspace as an environment of particular interest.

Figure 14. We looked at images of Karen's desk, where we circled certain objects and looked at where they were placed in relation to one another. We saw a cluttered, ever-changing assortment of objects, and knew we wanted to explore this further with Karen herself. We felt that participatory interviews (Kolb, 2008) after deployment were a crucial step in our research process, giving us the opportunity to collaboratively review photographs and offer a space for reflection on them (Harper, 2002).

INTERVIEWS

Figure 15. How did a participant perceive a particular environment or experience? How did they feel? For example, Karen shared with us that she constantly changes the arrangement of objects on her desk, as she gets 'manic and frustrated' by her working space. She is continuously trying to find a better way of arranging her belongings to make her working space 'feel better.' Reviewing images of her workspace together provided a prompt to talk about how she felt in that environment, and comment on particular different arrangements of objects; we saw potential in a scenario like this to feed directly into design inspiration for one's personal workspace.

LEARNINGS

Figure 16. What can we take away from the Auto-Cam project as design researchers? We saw the value of first-person, automatic photos in our visual analysis, looking at photographs that gave us a personal look at how someone went through their daily activities, seeing it from their perspective. We also felt the participant interview was a crucial stage in the process, opening up conversation and reflection on lived experiences, using the Auto-Cam photographs as a reference point. Using coloured stickers to 'tag' objects also allowed for a new kind of collaboration with participants, involving them in the process of determining what would trigger a photograph, giving them an interesting degree of agency in what images are captured.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Figure 17. Going forward, we'd like to iterate on our prototype paying attention to several aspects of the design (in terms of size, usability, and aesthetics). We also want to focus on providing a structured framework and method for how to choose with participants what objects are 'tagged' with stickers (can it be random? should some objects be assigned?). We only scratched the surface in terms of experimenting with how to incorporate sensors, and we'd like to look further at how a temperature sensor or heart rate sensor for example could be incorporated as an additional valuable layer to the visual research the Auto-Cam carries out. Overall, we look forward to exploring further the design space of autonomous POV cameras, which we believe will open a new genre of visual research for design.

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The emotional value of Do-It-Yourself materials

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Abstract It is known in the field of design, that when a project comes to shape, an emotional value of the designer or the team of designers that put together all the elements for the project to be born, it is and will be always something that artificiality and industry will never be able to meet. Imagine for a moment that even before the project comes as an idea, the designer is able to create a material that may be the perfect match for that idea to arise into a project. This pictorial is presented as a way to evidence the valuable contribute that material experience through the concept of Do-It-Yourself Materials is providing nowadays to designer's research. It is an approach to understand what is happening when everything starts with the material in mind before the project. By a meticulous interrogation to design students during the development of a material, a collection of experiences and a visual storytelling of a Do-It-Yourself Materials are presented to elucidate the importance of the meaning that the designer provides when, as an alchemist gains control of the material through interacting with it, how that meaning is carried within the material and therefore can be transferred to the project subsequently throughout an established vision.

Keywords *Material driven design, DIY materials, Material tinkering*

Introduction

Do-it-Yourself practices in the field of design happens since the origin of the discipline itself. Craftsmanship (Nimkurlat, 2010 p. 75), Bricolage (Louridas, 1999 p. 2) and experimentation (Ayala, 2014) have been always evident procedures for design professionals when arising a project. However, there has been for some time in the field of design a more noticeable need to contribute more deeply and in a robust way in research through these type of approaches. As design is considered a practice based branch of knowledge, a novel form of carrying out research in the field of materials is presented.

In the following pages, a visual storytelling of a *Do-It-Yourself-Materials (DIY-M)* practice (Rognoli, et. al, 2015) will be revealed. A course inside a *Master's Level Degree* was set as a pilot study where the *DIY-M* could be created and tested. Accompanying the path with a methodology known as *MDD or Material Driven*

Design (Karana, et. al, 2015), the outcome, shows visually how even before the project comes as an idea, the designer, through tinkering with materials without a project in mind but following a conscious method of research, is able to create a vision with the material that becomes for certain, a valuable contribute to create meaningful material experiences for the further project.

During the development of the course, one of the core facts that is also intended to be presented through this pictorial, is the emotional change of perception on the topic of *DIY-M* from the beginning, through and towards the end of the course of study. In the beginning, the course was perceived as another practical way to develop a project where experimenting with materials had non added value practice for a designer.

Figure 1. In the beginning of the course, the approach of the students towards the method was equivalent to any kind of design project. No emotional value through material experimentation was present.

For many of the students the concept of *Practice-Led Research* (Mäkela, 2007) (Pedgley, et. al, 2015), was far or unknown probably based on the fact that digital sources for design and non material theoretical approaches are abundant in the design education arena for the past decade. Also seeing that for

students the idea of hands-on project most of the time was associated with development of mock-ups or prototypes for a project. Once the students were immersed into the development of the materials throughout the method, a different, positive atmosphere started to be revealed.

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Figure 2. The first experimentations with materials following the MDD method, started to stimulate the students even if no considerable path appeared visible.

Students were given the chance to select from the MDD method one of the possible scenarios of development.

As all the students selected the third approach, namely,

[Scenario 3]

Designing with a material proposal with semi-developed or exploratory samples (e.g., food waste composites, living materials made of bacterial cells, 3D printed textiles, flexible OLEDs, etc.).

only the first part of the MDD method became the focus of study.

Figure 3. The more experimentations with material sources, the more emotionally engaged the students became.

Figure 4. Once the material experimentation was advancing, multi sensorial approaches were emerging throughout the analysis. Every material piece was evaluated and categorized accordingly to the method.

Figure 5. Every group of students once engaged with the method, began a continuous back and forth experimentation and collection of samples. With this amount of sources made, a flux in the Do-it-Yourself Materials process began.

Figure 6. The Do-It-Yourself Material Samples were tested with users in order to provide sensorial an perception feedback for further development.

Figure 7. Final presentation of the Do-It-Yourself Materials process. Apart from the material samples, printed formats with data collected and research evolution completed the delivery.

Figure 8. As the method requires to project a vision, a set up that illustrate the value and potential of the project was also presented.

Figure 9. Every group of students presented the Do-It-Yourself materials result according with their projected vision.

Figure 10. Possible paths for product development were also addressed by students.

Figure 11. What once during the process was conceived as a mistake, took value at the end of the course where “previous errors” provide different approaches and changes of perspective for further projects.

Figure 12. Some reactions of the material samples or transformations in time due to environmental conditions can also suggest possible paths of applications.

Recent contributions have proven that when it comes to the materiality, sensorial characterization and the material experiences that are developed through the experimentation with the material are most of the time present without a method (Karana, et.al, 2015) and therefore *Do-It-Yourself-Materials* (coined originally in our research as *DIY-M*) practices or self produced material experimentations with a lack of

method can not be considered research. Without the awareness that a specific methodology provides, several approaches to a *Do-It-Yourself-Materials* project that emerges with *material tinkering* (Jacobsson, 2013) will be recognized as purely experimentation. All experiences and sensorial relationships with a material when designing will be most of the time invisible for the designer as well.

Figure 13. Some material development suggests based on the material language outcome, possible further product development.

Some authors argue that the way artists and designers connect themselves to the field of research has been referred as "Practice-Led Research" (Mäkela, 2007), where looking at the process itself and the works produced to it will form a central part in the research itself. Cross devised on the other hand that because the world of doing and making is prior to understanding, the physical approach to research is important. accordingly,

The knowledge of design resides in people (designers), in the processes and in the product themselves (Cross, 1982 p.223).

Connected to Cross, a contemporary opinion adds to the topic the notion of craft, explaining that craft is a mean for logically thinking through senses (Nimkurlat, 2010 p. 75). Entering therefore into the world of sensorial understanding of things as a mean for designers to do research, Nimkurlat states that in textiles and other material designated disciplines, craft is understood not only as a way of making things by hand, but also a way of thinking through the hand

manipulation of a material (Nimkurlat, 2010 p. 64).

With notions of craftsmanship, sensorial and material exploration, is fundamental for this pictorial to address briefly also the theory around *Do-It-Yourself* practices as a way to understand the presented work. Quoting a definition of *DIY* practices as any creation, modification or repair action without the aid of professionals (Kuznetsov & Paulos, 2010) is important to underline that one of the drivers of the ongoing research on the matter believes that the *DIY* subculture is able to do things that work the same or better than the classical infrastructure of the society (Lukens, 2013 p.4). Thus an emerging way of experimenting with materials, namely to Do-It your own materials as a practice led research for designers, is being presented as another direction to follow in the evolution of the design discipline.

Students as shown in figures two to seven, driven by the possibility that *DIY-M* could make the difference and possibly work better than traditional scientific selection of materials approach, were gaining self

confidence around the proposition of a material once the method evidenced possible directions of development. The more experimentations with the material were performed, the better understanding of the sensorial properties and the connection to the vision appeared visible.

Once the final material developed was presented at the end of the course of study, the connection with the material and the vision was clear. What it has been perceived as an outcome after experienced the *DIY-M* path was not only a completely change of perception by the designer around the topic, but a fully positive emotional appreciation of the experimenting path of self fabrication of materials and the *Done-By-Yourself-Material* Outcome. As it will be possible to appreciate in figures eight to thirteen, the presented final result of the course is strongly connected with the firmly intention to continue the design process inspired by the designed material and the vision, different from when the material is simply selected from an existing collection. To conclude, we believe that the emotion changes when the designer sees from its own hands what it was able to create, when in the material itself the history of its creation is evident. As it has been visible in other researches, DIY practices carries within a state of affection stronger to the produced artifact than standard selection of components for the project (Salvia, 2015).

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Tactile explorations in a codesign project involving people with dementia

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Abstract This pictorial shows the process of involving a lady with advanced dementia and her husband, her main carer, in a design project, and discusses its implications, namely the need of an open and flexible approach to participatory design and the difficulties of interpreting and evaluating non-verbal responses. This work is part of a practice-based doctoral research that explores how design can enable people with dementia and their close social circle to develop personalised strategies communication, with a special focus on leisure and entertainment.

Keywords *Participatory design, Dementia care, Advanced dementia, Tactile stimulation*

Introduction

Dementia is a syndrome that progressively affects cognitive functions such as communication, reasoning and memory, compromising the ability to perform daily tasks, and having an adverse impact on relationships. This work is part of a practice-based doctoral research that explores how design can enable people with dementia and their close social circle to develop personalised strategies communication, with a special focus on leisure and entertainment. Personalisation, used here as “designing or changing (something) for a particular person” (Merriam-Webster, 2016), is seen as a way of addressing the underlying diversity of the experiences of dementia and to provide opportunities for meaningful communication.

In this research, people with dementia are invited to take part in the project, so their voices and their experiences are acknowledged throughout the process and in the results. In order to bridge the pronounced differences between the experience of people with dementia and the one of the designer, this research uses an approach based on empathy (Lindsay et al., 2012; Wallace et al., 2013). This approach is also deeply influenced by the *person-centred care* values, consisting of acknowledging everyone uniqueness as individuals independently of their age and ability, the effort to understand their perspective of the world, respecting and maintaining their *personhood* — a relational sense of self that is conferred by others — (Kitwood, 1997) — which is achieved by promoting vivid social environments and relationships, through

meaningful communication (Brooker, 2007). These attitudes are crucial to ensure that the main psychological needs of people with dementia—comfort, attachment, inclusion, occupation and identity, and an overall need for love—are met (Brooker, 2007; Kitwood, 1997). Ethical concerns are present throughout the whole process so that participants’ needs are respected, and potentially paternalistic attitudes avoided (Cowdell, 2006).

The preliminary phase of this research consisted of an observation-based study in two care institutions dealing with people with dementia, where the researcher assisted several activity sessions. The direct contact with several individuals with dementia, and the observation of how they engaged, participated and enjoyed these activity sessions, were essential to have a deeper understanding and develop empathy towards different experiences of living with this condition, leading to an enhanced sensibility and ethical awareness on how to work with this group of people (Figure 1).

The observation and learning resultant from this first interaction were crucial to define the next steps of research, consisting of bringing together people with dementia and their social circle to codesign personalised strategies for communication. Three previously designed ludic artefacts (Figure 2) were used as a starting point to invite people to participate in this project. These artefacts were designed to be left open for personalisation so that content could be

selected and adapted for and by the person with dementia and their family members. Participants were asked to personalise one of these artefacts if they found it interesting and adequate. Alternatively, participants were invited to engage in the definition of

a design brief according to their needs and preferences, and consequent design process. The following work, still in progress, illustrates one of these latter cases, involving a lady with advanced dementia and her husband, her main carer.

Figure 1. Activity sessions observed during the preliminary study included cognitive stimulation, reminiscence activities, music, arts and crafts and sensory stimulation.

Figure 2. The three artefacts open for personalisation: a book and a card game developed in previous research (Branco, 2014); and a board game, which was an outcome of the observation period (Branco, Quental, & Ribeiro, 2015).

Defining a design brief

Amelia and Gabriel¹ attend the day centre and have domiciliary care services provided by one of the institutions where the observation was conducted. Amelia is in an advanced stage of dementia and has nearly no verbal communication. Nevertheless, she intensively communicates non-verbally through facial expressions, gestures and body posture. The couple frequently participates in the activity sessions at the institution. Although not being actively engaged in the exercises proposed, Amelia often shows non-verbal signs of enjoyment, namely when sessions involve music and singing along, and when groups of little children were brought to participate in the activities.

After a year of being acquainted with the couple, they were invited to participate in this research project. The project was introduced and the three artefacts shown to Gabriel, who did not find any of the artefacts adequate for Amelia, due to her cognitive impairment. Therefore, we advanced with the definition of a design brief that could suit the needs and preferences of the couple. In this first meeting, opportunities were already identified: something to be used during the weekend, when the couple is at home and is less supported; something to entertain and stimulate Amelia, since she can be agitated while Gabriel prefers to watch TV or read. Gabriel was asked about using music to engage Amelia since it was clear from previous observations that she reacts very positively to it. Gabriel agreed and mentioned that they sometimes listen to music, but he does not like singing and would prefer something quieter.

Two exercises for a personalised design brief

Two exercises were created to support the personalisation of the design brief. These were drawn on the *person-centred thinking tools* (Bailey & Sanderson, 2013), used by dementia services to gather

information in order to deliver individualised care. The first one is about the weekly routine of the person with dementia and their close family, in order to identify plausible opportunities of use (Figure 3). The other exercise asks about how a perfect day and a bad day would be like for both the person diagnosed and the main family carer (Figure 4). The goal was to understand what is important for both: things they like and dislike doing, their interests and preferences, so that these were taken into consideration in design ideation.

The insights of the previous meeting were confirmed and the “perfect day” exercise regarding Amelia pointed to the possibility of exploring tactile stimulation with textiles since she used to love knitting and lace making. Gabriel added that she always took care of laundry and clothes and, even today, if she sees clothes she likes to touch them. The idea of tactile stimulation was also associated with the researcher’s observation of how Amelia would take her hand and “explore it” tactually, pressing each finger one by one, and sometimes the whole hand.

Although Amelia was present, it was not possible for her to respond to the exercises therefore, Gabriel answered for both. These exercises were crucial to deepen the available knowledge of the couple and to give directions on how to start, but it was clear that if Amelia was to be engaged in the design process, it should not imply any verbal activities, but instead giving her things to try out and observe how she non-verbally reacted.

rotina familiar	segunda-feira	terça-feira	quarta-feira	quinta-feira	sexta-feira	sábado	domingo
manhã	levantar após higiene D. Maria cabeleira no salão - Est a casa 8.30/8.45	levantar 11. - 12h grupo de canto - AS	levantar atividade D. Ana	levantar missa às 10h	levantar	levantar após higiene D. Maria limpeza casa	levantar
tarde	almoço 12. / 12.30	almoço	almoço	almoço	almoço	almoço	almoço ouvir a wista das 11. 10 - TV1
noite	jantar por volta das 19h cabeleira casa - AS deitar D. Maria às 7.00 notificação de deitar	jantar	jantar	jantar	jantar	jantar	jantar às vezes a filha passa a deitar
	deitar	deitar	deitar	deitar	deitar	deitar após higiene	deitar

Figure 3. Weekly routine exercise. This material served to note down details of the couple’s weekly routine to find out possible opportunities for use. The couple attends the day centre every day, except for the weekend when they stay at home.

1 The real names of participants have been replaced to preserve anonymity.

Figure 4. Amelia's perfect day exercise. This exercise consists of planning a 'perfect day'. A set of questions helps to guide the exercise: 1. How is the weather like? 2. What do I do? 3. With whom? 4. Where am I? 5. What do I see? 6. What do I eat? 7. How do I feel? Cues are provided to assist the response to questions 1 and 2, as well as blank cards for what people wish to add. The activities for the day are placed according to the daily moments, and the answers to the other questions are noted down around them, on the main page or on coloured post-its. The bad day exercise used the same materials but ended up being replaced only by an orange post-it. Since the perfect day exercise was already lengthy, and, in general, participants did not feel like thinking about a bad day and only referred some things they dislike.

In Amelia's case, the activities were placed randomly according to what Gabriel said she liked. Amelia likes having the attention from other people. She used to enjoy watching TV, she always loved to sing and dance, but Gabriel says it is more difficult now. However, she still enjoys music very much. When they are at home, she enjoys being at the window watching the children playing football in the backyard. She used to love knitting and lace-making but does not do it anymore. Amelia gets very happy when others treat her well, and despite her impairments, she is able to distinguish who cares for her or not.

Gabriel enjoys going to the day centre every day and spending the day with his friends. He enjoys watching the mass on TV, on Sunday. Sometimes, in the day centre, he is asked to bake cakes, which he loves due to his first job as a confectioner. He really enjoys to go on tours the day centre organises. In the evening, he enjoys watching the news on TV or reading the newspaper, and sometimes listening to the radio on his stereo. The fact that her wife is ill makes him very sad.

Development of an artefact for tactile stimulation using textiles

Since the work with textiles is out of the field of expertise of the researcher, a fashion designer was invited to collaborate. To the proposal of designing an artefact for tactile stimulation that was aesthetically pleasing, adequate, and dignifying for a lady in her 70s, the fashion designer suggested that it could also have a useful purpose, serving as a piece of clothing.

Bearing in mind the difficulty of involving Amelia in activities that required verbal communication, we have started by giving her different fabric samples and observe how she reacted to them (Figures 5). Amelia was entertained for nearly an hour in this activity. She was visibly happy, smiling and laughing at times. Amelia seemed to have a preference for soft

and warm fabrics, namely the ones with lighter colours. She would often join together two or more fabrics, and would spend some time feeling them and twisting them.

Drawing on this experience, the fashion designer suggested two ways of combining different fabrics that allow each material to be touched individually on both sides, using circles and using rings. These options were given to Amelia to try, who tactually explored both during some time, and seemed happy while doing it (Figures 6, 7).

We have observed that, when seated, Amelia usually places her hands on her legs, and did the same with the fabrics. Therefore, a blanket or a shawl that reached her lap, which served both to make her warm

and for stimulation, were thought to be the best option. A prototype was produced, using the circles combination, and was brought to Amelia. She looked tired on that day but engaged with touching the different fabrics of the prototype for a while. Having it

on her lap made the various textures more accessible to her hands than having it on her back, as a shawl, where she would only reach the ends of the prototype (Figure 8).

Figure 5. Amelia sensing, moving and twisting different fabrics, and example of the notes of Amelia's reactions.

Amelia's reactions were noted for each sample: how she touched them, moved them, fold them, with one hand, two hands, fingers, how she placed them on her legs, how she combined them, how long she kept them, if she didn't seem to care too much, if she grabbed it from the researcher's hand, etc.

Figure 6. Sample of the combination of different fabrics composed by same-size circles. This combination allows the different fabrics to be touched on both sides, even in a bigger piece, through the holes between the circles, enabling more exploration. The flat circles, permitting to clearly see each fabric, can also work as a visual stimulus namely if a bigger variety of fabrics is combined.

Figure 7. Sample of the other combination of different fabrics, using rings within a chain structure. This combination is visually more confusing, but has more movement if swung, possibly provoking a more synesthetic experience. The several rings allow fingers and hands to pass through them, as well as turning and twisting, prompting exploration.

Figure 8. Prototype using circles combination, intended to be worn as a shawl or as a blanket. If used as a shawl, most of the different fabrics were not reachable to Amelia's hands. Therefore, in order to provide a more active stimulation, it was better to use the prototype as a blanket.

Preliminary results – inclusive tactile emotions

In order to better, and externally, evaluate the work developed, the psychologist of the institution was consulted. In her opinion, focusing on a tactile stimulus for Amelia was appropriate and pertinent. The clinician valorised the prototype developed for promoting tactile stimulation that enables exploration and discovery, and for the possibility of being worn, offering involvement, comfort, warmth, which can induce positive emotions and the sensation of protection. In her words she highlighted such gains: *"It seems to me that, in this way, you are able to offer the sensation of protection and warmth which is searched by people with dementia (...) it seems able to become a facilitator of a more positive emotional environment. If we get warmer through our emotions, we are then more available to what surrounds us"* (the institution's psychologist, personal communication, March 16, 2016).

The ring combination was also appreciated for being more playful. It was suggested that both combinations can serve different stimulation moments, with distinct forms of use. The circle combination can promote a relaxing stimulation while the ring combination can provide more active one. Textures could be, in general, more varied, and soft and muted colours are adequate, namely in the case of the calmer circle combination. In the ring combination, more vivid colours could be

used, but being aware of over-stimulation. The psychologist found the results adequate and not infantilised, aesthetically pleasing and attractive, stimulating and playful, suggesting that they could be tried with other people with advanced dementia. In addition, she valued the inclusion of Amelia in this process, referring that in the institution they have noticed that Amelia is more involved with the several things they use for stimulation, that she seems more confident, and that through that she started relating more with other people: *"(...) now we notice much more involvement [of Amelia] with the diverse elements [for stimulation]. I think that we should attribute, or at least equate, that this is a result of your work with her. From this exploration, she starts feeling more confident, and she then starts looking for more, isn't it? (...) and with this, she started to involve herself more with others"* (the institution's psychologist, personal communication, March 16, 2016).

These insights were embedded in further developments of two artefacts. The comfort and warmth characteristics were enhanced in a new prototype, which evolved to a poncho with the circle combination of different textile textures at the front (Figure 9). The ring combination was crocheted, since it allows other kinds of textures and could possibly trigger some reminiscence, and used more vivid colours for a more active stimulation (Figure 10).

Figure 9. New prototype using circles combination in a poncho. The circles were only included on the front of the piece, where Amelia's hands could reach them. We have included a bigger variety of fabrics, selecting those that have distinct textures on both sides, and colours, keeping them within a calm/muted spectrum so that a relaxing stimulation can be provided.

Figure 10. Prototype using rings combination. With the purpose of promoting a more active stimulation, vivid colours were chosen for this piece.

Amelia wore the poncho for about an hour. She was well during this time, always entertained touching the circles, passing from one circle to the other and feeling them on both sides, sometimes also putting her hands in between them. From time to time, she stopped with her hands and looked carefully at the circles.

It was only possible to observe Amelia interaction with the crocheted ring combination for a short time, but she did explore the different textures in the ring. The fact that she offered resistance when the caregiver tried to take it from her hands is also a hint that she was probably enjoying it. Moreover, this piece, probably for the vivid colours but also for the strangeness and non-identifiable shape, aroused interest from other people in the room, who also wanted to play with it. Another lady was visibly enthusiastic about this piece and kept it and explored it for a while.

Discussion

Involving people with dementia in a participatory design process is challenging, not only due their different experience of the world but also due to the methods used, which rely on the use of verbal and visual prompts, compromising their participation. Therefore, in order to include people with cognitive impairment, participation needs to be perceived more broadly, and processes need to be highly individualised and adjusted (Hendriks, Slegers, & Duysburgh, 2015; Wallace et al., 2013). In this case, it was crucial to adopt a flexible and open attitude that accommodated the participants' needs and preferences, firstly to ensure a personalised brief and results, and secondly, so that the person with dementia and her carer could participate how they felt at ease. Also, knowing the couple beforehand, during the preliminary phase of this study facilitated their

involvement and being comfortable with the researcher (McCarthy & Wright, 2015).

Since verbal communication was required, the initial approach and the two exercises were developed only with Gabriel, who shared his expertise in knowing, living and caring for Amelia. These valuable insights allowed us to grasp what is important to both, pointing directions to understand where to start and formulate a design brief. After this, it was possible to invite Amelia to participate in the process through developing activities that did not require any verbal communication. By these means, the design proposal emerged from experiences shared by Gabriel and from the non-verbal reactions of Amelia to the samples, both having a crucial influence on the design ideation and prototype development.

As pointed out by Hendriks et al. (Hendriks et al., 2015), one of the main challenges of involving people with cognitive impairments in the design process is how to analyse non-verbal data. It is difficult to evaluate whether the use of such tactile stimulus is beneficial for Amelia. She has demonstrated to engage with tactually exploring the different fabrics, and she has shown signs of enjoyment, through smiles and laughing, and at the end of the first session, by suddenly standing up and hugging the researcher. Gabriel perceived it differently. He apologised for her wife, for not demonstrating more interest in samples and prototypes that were brought to her, thus preferring not to keep the prototype. Nonetheless, he always showed a willingness to participate and esteemed the company and attention given to the couple throughout the process. The comments and observation of the psychologist were crucial to understand the adequacy of the brief proposed, the importance of involving Amelia in the process, and the

possibility that the results are not only relevant for her, but also for other people in similar stages of dementia.

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Embracing ambiguity: Five types of ambiguity encountered in product design

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Abstract This paper visually and theoretically explores the benefits of ambiguity in experience-driven design. A visual search has been conducted to discover how ambiguity is applied among designers and used as a resourceful tool to create novel experiences for users. We propose that ambiguity can create a sense of intriguing familiarity for users. Furthermore we theoretically explain why, how, and when ambiguity occurs during interactions with products. As a result we present five types of ambiguity (perceptual, functional, prototypical, referential, emotional) arising from perceptual, cognitive, and emotional processing of products. The theoretical findings are visually presented and good visual examples are provided for different types of ambiguity encountered in product design.

Keywords *Ambiguity, Product design, Meaning attribution, Affective response*

Introduction

Among designers and engineers, ambiguity has always been a topic to avoid for the sake of facilitating smooth human-product interactions and ease in product use. Unlike the practices in different fields of art, which make use of ambiguity frequently to evoke intriguing and engaging art experiences, the potentials of ambiguity in product design and what it can offer users as a 'special' product experience have been rarely explored. To our knowledge, Gaver, Beaver, and Benford (2003) are among the first to embrace ambiguity as a rich resource for designing human-computer interactions and to offer design strategies to enhance, create or provoke ambiguity when designing information, context, and relationships. Alex Zakkas (2013) explored how ambiguity could induce creativity when people interacted with, and made use of, an object that is abundant in our lives, i.e., a twig. Product designers such as Philippe Starck also explored ambiguity in their work. Starck's Juicy Salif, with its unconventional features for a lemon juicer, has dual-functionality envisioned by the designer: one being a lemon squeezer, the other being a conversation starter in awkward moments (Lloyd & Snelders, 2003).

Although foundations of ambiguity have not been theoretically studied in the field of experience design, designers seem to have been exploring the potentials of ambiguity in practical ways in order to provide users with novel and exciting experiences. With this paper we aim to demonstrate several uses of ambiguity in product design, systematically categorize the examples of ambiguous products, and support our visual findings with theoretical insights.

Examples of product ambiguity and theoretical foundations

By definition, anything that is ambiguous is open to more than one interpretation and does not have a fixed meaning. The process of discovery of meaning is

therefore an exciting and rewarding moment for the user who is interacting with an ambiguous object. Such discovery also implies a personal significance, a secret and intimate relationship between the object and the person. Furthermore, resolving ambiguity not only activates processes of meaning attribution but also affective processes pertaining to aesthetic appreciation and emotions. On a functional level of product experience, ambiguity can leave the door open to interpretation in order to spark users' creativity and ingenuity in discovering and exploring novel / genuine uses and contexts for the product.

Our visual perception constantly detects and identifies objects through categorization. The process of object identification consists of three consequential sub-processes. These are *perception*, *cognition* and *appraisal* leading for *emotional response*. **Perceptual processes** try to make sense of the object form, thus it is an internal search to find a match within visual memory (does this object exist?). Perceptual processes may also give rise to sensory pleasure as in aesthetic appreciation. Upon perception, **cognitive processes** try to make sense of the object identity; thus it is a categorical search within the repertoire of well-established concepts (what exactly is this object?). Upon cognition, **emotional processes** take over in order to assign the beneficial value (good / bad) of the object; thus, it is a search for a right response (how should I act? Approach or avoid?).

Ambiguity is fundamentally a glitch in the process of object identification. Theoretically, we see three possibilities for ambiguity to take place: *i.* the inherent properties of the object does not give rise to any recognition in the perceiver (i.e., **perceptual ambiguity**); *ii.* upon object perception, cognitive processes give rise to many different conceptual associations (i.e., **cognitive ambiguity**); and *iii.* upon cognition, appraisal component of emotional

processes give rise to conflicting responses / actions (i.e., **emotional ambiguity**). In all cases, the object fails to be identified or responded in one correct way. In perceptual ambiguity, an object cannot be identified because it cannot be categorized into one single category. In cognitive ambiguity, an object can be identified, but in multiple ways because the object can be categorized into more than one category. In emotional ambiguity, an object is identified but multiple needs and goals might be conflicting and therefore evoking positive and negative responses towards the object.

Considering the three levels of ambiguity, we have explored good examples for ambiguity used in product

design (see Figure 1). Our visual research has yielded results other than the three levels (see Figure 2). While we found fitting examples for Perceptual and Emotional ambiguity, Cognitive ambiguity yielded three sub-categories: Functional, Prototypical and Referential. In *Functional* ambiguity, an ambiguous product can fit on more than one product category depending on the use context of the product. In *Prototypical* ambiguity, a product does not visually fit in a product category but functionally fits in that category. In *Referential* ambiguity, more than two object categories become active, one pertaining to a product category, one pertaining to a distant and conceptually irrelevant category exhibiting a metaphorical connection.

Figure 1. A random collection ambiguous products.

Figure 2. Listed above are examples of the five types of ambiguity submitted by students of the Delft University of Technology, Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering, Master program of Design for Interaction for the class of Product User Understanding and Experience (2015). The assignment given to the students consisted of searching and submitting examples of objects that, in their opinion, reflected upon the five types of ways an object can facilitate ambiguity in terms of the definitions listed early on in the pictorial.

Five types of product ambiguity

What arises from the formulation of these five types of ambiguity is the specific experience and interaction style each type requires from the user. See Figure 3

Perceptual ambiguity causes intrigue from the user, exhilarates them to approach and interact with the ambiguous object in a curious manner as in to discover its identity and purpose. The aesthetical quality of these objects is very appealing and highly pleasant. See Figure 4 for an example.

Functional ambiguity causes the user to explore the potential possibilities the object affords in their interactions to fulfill a specific need (interactions as in affordances). With this type of ambiguity, users have a sense of achievement when they define their own way of using the product. They feel satisfied and proud. See Figure 5 for an example.

Prototypical ambiguity specifically focus upon stretching the user's expectancies of how an object in its own category should look, function, and be experienced as. It provides users with novel experiences with existing functions. Users need to update the product category in which the ambiguous object naturally fits. See Figure 6 for an example.

Referential ambiguity builds on metaphorical relationships between objects in order to convey a

message in the form of other object. Users refer to their past experiences and interactions with other object categories. Users may feel puzzled to figure out the duality in meaning, but eventually feel successful when they reach a verdict. See Figure 7 for an example.

Emotional ambiguity revolves around the emotional experience the object elicits in the user. This type of ambiguity is driven by the either contradicting or divergent possibility of both positive and negative emotions the user experiences while interacting with said ambiguous object. See Figure 8 for an example.

5 TYPES OF HOW OBJECTS FACILITATE AMBIGUITY

Figure 3. The above figure visualises how objects can facilitate ambiguous experiences between users and objects via the five types depicted above. Aesthetic ambiguity concerns the user's perception of the object in terms of stimuli that causes them to approach and interact. Proto-typical, Referential, and Functional ambiguity pertain to the processes of meaning attribution the user conveys on to the object resulting in its appraisal. Lastly Emotional ambiguity delves into the conflicting emotional responses user's experience when interacting with the object.

Figure 4. **Perceptual Ambiguity.** Phontonic is a connected polygo-nal shaped handheld device that plays sound in accordance the how the user interacts with it. The aesthetic of the device gives no direct hints as to what its function is, it is only when the user begins to interact with the device they discover the possibilities.

Figure 5. **Functional ambiguity.** TU Delft Interactive Sound Chair. The object in itself affords a variety of possible seating postures for the user to experience. To go alongside this the object becomes dependent on the user in order to achieve the full interaction experi-ence. The chair achieves this by requiring the users to connect with each other and the object in specific manners to generate sound in a multitude ways. Students can also use the chair as a back support, a table, a shelf increasing its functional use.

Figure 6. **Prototypical Ambiguity.** Hovding's "Airbag for Cyclists". The category for what a bicycle helmet consists of as well as for the category of a scarf are stretched in terms of the user's perception of their typical "conceptual model" of either due to their physical and functional properties. Utilising imagery from the other's conceptual model and melding them together has resulted in Hovding creating a cycling helmet and scarf that is not only unlike any other but as well creating new interpretations and interactions with both by the user.

Figure 7. Referential Ambiguity. Joseph Joseph's Wash Line Pin Product. The physical exterior of the object resembles the image of a sunflower with a number of petals. As the user requires the use of each individual pin, the interaction resembles that of plucking the petals off of a flower. This poetic metaphor calls upon past experiences the user may have undergone from another category, in this case plucking flowers, to drive how they interpret their interactions and experience with the object.

Figure 8. Emotional Ambiguity. The toilet brush Excalibur by Philippe Starck represents a toilet cleaning tool that is functional, dirty, unpleasant etc. While in conjunction with the affective meanings associated with a knights lance; valiant, heroic, and aggressive, the toilet brush then becomes a sort of heroic weapon against dirtiness by giving the user a heroic feeling while performing a disgusting chore of cleaning the toilet.

Figure 9. Kitchen utensil built to exhibit the five types of ambiguity stated earlier. (from left to right: perceptual (A), functional (B), prototypical (C), referential (D), and emotional (E)).

Figure 10. Pictured above is the user test seeking to gauge how users (the participants) perceive, give meaning to, and emotionally respond to the five objects conveying the five different types of ambiguity.

Designing with product ambiguity

Through the utilization of these five types of ambiguity, designers not only open up the possibility to create deeper meaningful experiences between the object and user but also discover new ways of playing with object perception and altering users expectations. As a result, designer master new methods for offering rich and novel experiences to users. From the users' perspective, the five types of ambiguity that an object can facilitate enables users to experiences the object in a way that is simultaneously intriguing and familiar. This intrigue experienced by the user is the break away from the expected, rather ordinary, experience they have of interacting with the object. The familiar aspect pertains to the interpretations the users utilise as a driving force to dictate how they interact with the object. These interpretations are what is personal and user specific and thus every user experiences varying interpretations of how they interact with an object. Thus ambiguous objects rather than seek to elicit a specific experience between the user and object look to leave themselves "open" to the users interpretation that drives how they interact with and experience the object on the levels of perception, cognition, and emotion.

The first author is currently designing a range of objects that exhibit these five types of ambiguity for his master thesis in design (See Figure 9 for an example for functional ambiguity). He aims to discover how designers can help users embrace these types of

ambiguity and how can ambiguity be included in the product design process as a whole. The expected date of completion of this thesis is March-April 2016. High quality prototypes will be available to present during the conference.

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Community in collaborative maker spaces

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Abstract This document describes an ongoing research project investigating the development of a sense of community in collaborative maker spaces. The document reports preliminary findings from a phenomenological inquiry into the nature of identity and interaction amongst artists-in-residence at Standard Projects, a small maker studio in Hortonville, Wisconsin, and the studio's broader social network. The document begins with an introduction to the project, which is followed by a series of annotated images from an interactive artwork (<http://quality.robertfraher.com>) that was created as an experiential representation of the knowledge derived from the study. The annotations describe the user experience and highlight aspects that exemplify the most prominent factors identified in community building. These factors are skill, instruction, and emotion.

Keywords *Interactive, Collaborative, Creative, Community, Instruction*

Introduction

I initially became interested in collaborative maker spaces when a colleague mentioned he was part of an all-night hack-a-thon hosted in Minneapolis, Minnesota to respond to the digital needs of area non-profit companies. I was fascinated by the notion of an informal, creative environment, seemingly unified by little more than a group's shared interest in making something. I wondered about how these entities came together, and what made them, and the individuals who constituted them, work effectively. Over time, my exposure to a variety of maker spaces, and my subsequent conversations with people involved in them, led me to a specific question, "What are the most significant factors in the emergence of a sense of community in collaborative maker spaces?"

This question became the basis of a phenomenological investigation into the nature of identity and interaction amongst individuals in collaborative maker spaces. To explore this question, I embedded myself as an artist-in-residence at Standard Projects, a small multidisciplinary maker studio in Hortonville, Wisconsin. The studio was started in 2014 by artist and designer Claire Abitz. My decision to use Standard Projects as the context for my inquiry was based on three characteristics of the studio, which I did not find elsewhere. First, the studio has a residency program. This attribute was primary in my decision-making, as I wanted to consider the studio's social structure and interpersonal dynamics from within that structure and with the ability to contribute to its dynamics. Second, the studio had been founded fairly recently. Due to this, I reasoned that its social network would still be emerging and thus, might provide more insightful observations related to the process of relationship building. Third, I saw evidence in the marketing and news content associated with the studio of an emphasis on sustainability and ecologically sensitive practices. I felt that, in this way, the value structure of the studio aligned with my own,

and therefore hoped this similarity would lead to productive interaction.

During August of 2015, I spent eight days living and working at Standard Projects. My activities during this time involved interviewing, collaborating, and socializing with the other artists-in-residence, as well as with many members of the studio's broader social network. Having reflected upon these experiences and compared my initial conclusions with those of others, three factors have emerged as being the most prominent in influencing the development of a sense of community at Standard Projects. These factors are skill, instruction, and emotion, described below.

Factors in community building

The factors described herein are three related ideas, and are understood to be influential in the development of a sense of community at Standard Projects. These ideas were identified based on experiential investigation and systematic reflection and corroboration with others. I present these ideas as categories of description, which are intended to generalize the knowledge derived from this inquiry to aid in understanding the development of a sense of community within other collaborative maker spaces.

Skill

Individual skill was understood as a major influence in how interpersonal relationships develop. The character of this skill can be analyzed along two main axes, the nature of an individual's skills (e.g., woodworking) and skill level (e.g., expert). During my time at the studio, no individual was considered to be the most proficient with all media or techniques. Instead, it was understood that each person brought to the enterprise either a unique level of competence with a particular process or material, or a breadth of knowledge that could be used to facilitate communication. Skill was identified as a primary determiner of opportunities for collaboration.

Instruction

The process of instruction was observed to happen almost perpetually during activities that involved collaboration. The sharing of knowledge also regularly occurred during periods of nonproductive time, or socialization. The axes along which the character of this idea can be analyzed include providing or receiving (e.g., teacher or learner), applied or conceptual (e.g., hands-on or hands-off), and detailed or general (e.g., in-depth or superficial). A strong correlation was observed between individuals who were active across any of these axes and their sense of place in the community.

Emotion

Perhaps the most telling factor identified, an individual's emotional relationship to his or her work was recognized as a ubiquitous trait amongst the individuals that comprise the studio's social network. The character of this emotional component can be analyzed across three main axes, empathic (e.g., relating to the needs of the user of the artifact being created), qualitative (e.g., describing the experience provided by an artifact), and intrinsic (e.g., an individual's internal motivation for creative activity). It became apparent that the emphasis given to the first two of these dimensions fluctuated based on what an individual was making. However, the last dimension was understood as foundational, and was described as influential regardless of an individual's project focus. Moreover, an individual's strong sense of intrinsic motivation was universally acknowledged as a quality important to others in the studio's social network.

Experiential representation of knowledge

Based on the insights described above, I proposed a collaborative project to the other artists-in-residence that would serve as an experiential representation of the knowledge derived from the study thus far. All of the artists elected to participate, as well as several others from the studio's broader social network. This project took the form of an interactive audio-visual documentary (<http://quality.robertfraher.com>).

This piece applies text from Christopher Alexander's *The Timeless Way of Building* as a narrative to guide users through the studio's maker spaces, between each of the artists-in-residence, and amongst the other social activities at the studio. Alexander's text was selected based on how its theoretical perspective aligns with that of the general ideology of the studio. Alexander (1979) describes his theoretical perspective as "an entirely new attitude to architecture and planning" (p. i). This attitude celebrates design and building processes that help people feel alive.

Alexander believes there is a central quality found in all the experiences that cause us to feel alive. He (1979) described this quality as "the quality without a name" (p. ix). This interactive artwork seeks to represent the creative processes and communal situations in which this quality is elicited and appreciated at Standard Projects. The images below are screenshots from the piece, and are accompanied by annotations describing the user experience and aspects that exemplify skill, instruction, and emotion.

Figure 1. The opening state of the composition uses atmospheric sounds and photography to create a sense of intrigue and establish a premise for the exploration to follow.

Figure 2. Upon the user's initial interaction, animated text continues the narrative as the context for exploration further develops with additional imagery and music.

Figure 3. Through subsequent user interaction, the composition leads users to a menu of situations to be investigated. Each of these situations employs a dynamic audio-visual format involving additional animated text, time-lapse photography, atmospheric sounds, and music.

Each of the situations represents an artist engaged in his or her creative process. These situations were conceived to demonstrate both an artist's high level of skill and passion for his or her craft.

Figure 4. The Sewing Room.

Figure 5. The Garage.

Figure 6. The Airstream.

Figure 7. The Study.

Figure 8. Claire Abitz.

Figure 9. Nic Langner.

Figure 10. Shannon Slane.

Figure 11. Robert Fraher.

Figure 12. When the user chooses to move on, the composition presents a dinner party sequence involving additional animated text, time-lapse photography, and music. This section also contains an audio recording of part of the dinner conversation, a candid example of informal instruction.

Figure 13. Dinner party continued.

Q

Figure 14. Dinner party continued.

Q

Figure 15. Dinner party continued.

Q

Figure 16. When the dinner party sequence concludes, users are presented with a final image and looping audio until they choose to progress.

Q

Figure 17. The composition then presents the next phase of the evening using additional animated text, time-lapse photography, and music. This section also contains an audio recording of a portion of the campfire discussion. Two designers discuss the subtleties new product characteristics. Two artists learn how to sing a song together.

Figure 18. The final phase of the composition presents the concluding text of the narrative, images of cut flowers, and music.

Figure 19. The composition contains an “about” section for users interested in learning more about the guiding text and / or the studio featured in the composition.

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Uncomfortable self-reflections: Confronting the social problems that graphic designers help to perpetuate

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Abstract Using methods of critical inquiry, American graphic design students confront uncomfortable realities about the role that brand identity plays in promoting and reinforcing detrimental attitudes and habits of American society and culture.

This initiative invites them to use their graphic design skills to critically examine American culture through the filter of their own personal experience in it. The students consider how brands can often exploit the society's insecurities and desires, selling them products, services, and ideas that they don't need or shouldn't accept. Mindful of the role that graphic designers play in the emergence of successful brands, the students create satirical brand identities for reprehensible companies of their own invention. This process makes use of the Culture Jamming process, which is 'the act of using existing mass media to comment on those very media themselves, using the original medium's communication method.'

Recent parody projects have explored obesity, prescription drugs, gender issues, xenophobia, climate ignorance, body image, and misogyny in entertainment. This initiative provides a model for educators looking for ways to incorporate cultural criticism into an already tightly defined curriculum.

Keywords Branding, Cultural criticism, Parody, Curriculum

Figure 1. Designer Ben Stokes is alarmed at the way that heroin has regained its popularity in the U.S. after years of oblivion, while at the same time de-criminalization and commercial availability of marijuana across the U.S. He wonders if the new Pot Shops will lead the way to the eventual legalization and acceptance of more harmful recreational drugs. His invented company, Quick Smack, parodies our American desire to have anything – even heroin – available for sale at a shop around the corner.

LOCK IT DOWN

Figure 2. Designer Jessie Fullerton is tired of American “rape culture” -- where victims of sexual assault are blamed for dressing too provocatively or tempting men with their sexuality. She parodies this with **Lock it Down**, her invented company that sells chastity belts, repellent sprays and hideous clothing meant to ‘protect’ women from violent sexual predators.

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REPLACEMENT

Figure 3. Designer Ann Kennedy wondered if the American pay inequities from men to women might be a bit too convenient for some employers, who favor female employees because they can be paid less. She invented **Replacemen**, a parody of an employment agency that supplies female workers to replace male workers at the bargain price of 70 cents on the dollar.

Figure 4. Designer Emily Werdal finds it ironic that Americans still hold to conventional attitudes about sexuality, specifically the double-standard that labels women as sluts if they have had multiple partners, while this is regarded as admirable in men. Her invented company *Screw Me* parodies this inconsistency by creating a dating service that ranks potential sex partners based on their desirability: females rank more highly if they are virginal, while men rank more highly if they have plenty of experience.

Figure 5. Designer Alex Flatness is disappointed in how many Americans have become addicted to video games, willingly isolating themselves from the rest of the world. She blames parents whose permissive attitudes promote gaming addiction in children. Her invented company is *Secluser*, a boarding facility where gaming addicts can live in seclusion without any connections to - or distractions from - their families or the real world.

Figure 6. Designer Lauren Juenger is critical of American cultures overreliance on prescription drugs for children, especially those that are used to treat Attention Deficit Disorder. She believes that many parents use these drugs simply to get their kids to conform to societal conventions, rather than any real concern about the medical diagnosis. With A.D.D. being diagnosed in American children at unprecedented rates, she sees this as a socially accepted method of behavior control. She invented **Kidformity**, a company that dispenses Adderall through vending machines without prescription, to parody just how far this problem could go.

Figure 7. Designer Dustin Edle is critical of the way that Americans seem oblivious to climate change and our dependence on fossil fuels. He invented **Desource**, a competition (similar to those on reality TV) that rewards people for being wasteful and thoughtless with their vehicle choices and fuel consumption.

Figure 8. Designer Lu Lawrence is astounded by how many Americans self-identify as an expert in something – simply from watching Youtube videos and surfing online info. She parodies this – as well as our willingness to believe dubious internet medical advice – with **Self Surgeon**, a company that provides you with the ‘expertise’ to perform your own surgeries at home – with all the predictable consequences.

Figure 9. Designer Alex Huston is critical of our culture’s obsession with personal re-invention. He invented **IdentiSwap**, a company that helps you to conduct identity theft for the purpose of advancing your personal destiny. Customers can then boast of their newly invented identities to others in the community who share their belief in perpetual re-invention of self.

Figure 10. Designer Brenda Baccam is critical of the relentless human compulsion to label and categorize people with exclusionary descriptors of race, ethnicity, personality, body type, and so on. She feels that these labels are an attempt by one person to categorize another in an effort to feel superior. She invented Label Me, a company that streamlines the labeling process by limiting the labels to simply acceptable and unacceptable. Not only are you now locked in, you aren't even sure what criteria were used to plant you in the yes or no category. You will now be treated by others simply as acceptable or unacceptable and will internalize this as your self-identity.

Graphic design students need opportunities to critically examine their future role in society. Will design always be a positive force? Or does it contribute to some of the problems of contemporary culture? Can a designer practice their profession in harmony with their personal ethics?

Yet students are rarely given the opportunity to explore these questions in their studio coursework. Busy as we are trying to cover an extensive list of learning objectives, its too convenient for professors to structure assignments to mimic the needs of the real world client: We can efficiently cover the course requirements when no one stops to ask **why?** What would happen if we spent time grappling with big ethical questions?

As students learn the basic components of graphic identity systems, they come to realize that **anything** can be effectively branded and marketed through the power of graphic design. This realization provides an opportunity to examine ethical questions: How is this cultural influence manifested in the design of global brands? Are the values of America's consumer culture being promoted to its citizens and throughout the world through the design of brand identity? If so, what is the responsibility of the graphic designer in this process? Does every commercial enterprise

deserve a great brand identity? Is it possible to put a pretty face on an ugly idea? Is a design solution successful if it contributes to the problems of society? Is it possible to create something beautiful for a client you abhor?

Unfortunately, few of these questions are being addressed in graphic design pedagogy. In the typical Branding Design assignment, for example, students learn how images carry meaning, and how to exploit that capability for a client's commercial needs. Can this capability be examined in terms of its global consequences? What if, instead of branding fashion, beauty products, electronics and other typical artifacts of consumer culture, the students were asked to **parody** that very culture? What if, instead of the conventional approach to branding, students created satirical branding campaigns for reprehensible clients as a way to explore the power of graphic identity? Instead of blindly embracing branding theory, could their introduction to the topic require them to develop skepticism towards its impact on American consumer culture?

This satirical branding project has 4 steps:

1. Begin by considering some aspects of contemporary American culture that you consider

to be troublesome to society. What is the role of branding in promoting these problems? How does a successful American brand act as an export of American ideology and culture?

2. Select a specific contemporary social problem that is upsetting or repugnant to you. Who is responsible for perpetuating this problem? How does the media make this problems worse? How much worse could this problem get?
3. Invent an absurd and fundamentally wicked corporation that would exploit this problem for its own commercial gain.
4. Create a satirical brand identity for your invented corporation, applying your brand image across a variety of promotional materials for the corporation.

Preliminary research includes the video *No logo*, a documentary featuring aspects of Naomi Klein's well-known book by the same title. It examines issues of social justice and global domination associated with the export of consumer culture through American brands. According to Klein, "The astronomical growth in the wealth and cultural influence of multinational corporations over the last fifteen years can arguably be traced back to a single, seemingly innocuous idea... that successful corporations must primarily produce brands, as opposed to products."

At the beginning of the assignment, students are introduced to the subversive practice of *culture jamming*, which is defined as the act of using existing mass media to comment on those very media themselves, using the original medium's communication method. It is based on the belief that advertising is little more than propaganda for established interests, and that there is little escape from this propaganda in industrialized nations. In his book *Rules for Radicals*, Saul Alinsky explains Culture jamming as "utilizing the power of one part of the power structure against another part...the superior strength of the Haves become their own undoing." In addition, the meaning of satire is discussed, which is defined by the *Oxford Dictionary* as..."the use of humor, irony, exaggeration, or ridicule to expose and criticize people's stupidity or vices, particularly in the context of contemporary politics and other topical issues."

As the students researched their topics, they are asked to write an essay that answers these questions:

- *What is the Real-life situation that prompts your parody?*
- *Who do you hold accountable?*
- *What's your concept for the parody?*
- *How is your concept ridiculous or absurd?*
- *How are you imitating the real-life situation?*
- *How are you making it obvious that it's satire?*

It seems to help when the students work from an existing conviction, as this provides extra motivation. In fact, this might be the key to the project's success: perhaps they all have a hot-button issue that will give them both conviction and confidence. For example, Jenna was still mourning the death of a high school friend from complications of bulimia when she

created a satirical brand on the topic. So the project was, in a sense, a labor of love. Feleecia has faced a lifetime of personal questions about her ethnicity, prompting her to make daring choices for her invented racial-profiling brand. And it seems clear that *all* of the females in class have personally felt the weight of our culture's impossible ideals of physical perfection. In fact, many of the topics chosen for this project involve personal and cultural identity, whether about race, the desire for attention, or giving birth to a child whose identity is predetermined and perfected. This interweaving of concepts of personal identity, cultural identity and brand identity enhanced the learning experience by pointing out the parallels across these divergent notions.

It is evident that our students have become pretty keen observers of the prevailing culture, and as much as we sometimes wonder about their generation, they have superb skills at cultural criticism. They also understand completely the learning objectives of the assignment, shown here in the words of the students:

"This project had two divergent and contradictory lessons. First, I learned how to think more conceptually and how to create a successful identity system. This project also caused me to think about personal ethics: as graphic designers we have a social responsibility to the world. While it is our job to create aesthetically appealing and conceptually sound designs, we must also decide where to draw the line. At what point should we say no to a company whose practices are less than desirable? This project encouraged us to think about the decisions we make and the clients we agree to work with." - Heidi Miller

"I started this project excited about the concept, confused, lost...mostly lost. There are so many wrongs in this world that could be addressed. Which one would work the best for the context of the project? The direction I started with...seemed fairly simple, and quite repulsive, as it should have. I believe what I have shown through [my satirical company] is the desire branding has to be seen as a helper of consumers, yet always keeping its own interests as the final goal. There may not be anything ultimately evil about this; however the means and ends need always to be kept in perspective." - Jonathan Rahmani

Personal digital manifestations - Contemporary digital life and the objects that enable it

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Abstract The manipulation and crafting of our physical environment is a fundamental and defining human characteristic. The standardized and mass produced urban civilizations we inhabit are becoming increasingly impersonal.

As we search for deeper connections and forge meaningful relationships with our environment we face new challenges of integrating the intangible digital content on which we place an increasing importance.

Through a process of enhancing and exaggerating the interaction process, the physicality of these digital devices may better describe the relationship between individuals and their digital content.

I endeavor to create objects that represent the intangible digital content they contain, in the hope they may take more aesthetic and meaningful forms to better integrate them into the most personal of environments, our homes.

Through this paper I will describe how I have sought to represent one of the most important aspects of individuality and self, expressed within our homes, memory.

Keywords *Kinesthetic, Memories, Tangible, Ritual, Interaction*

Digital intersection

Our homes are often considered refuge from modernity, from the frantic pace and the myriad of distractions in our daily life. An escape from the inhumane offices, factories, and industrial parks of our urbanized environment, however machines have crept in from these domains to offer our personal lives contemporary technological equivalents to the analogue objects with which we have traditionally adorned our personal spaces.

Figure 1. Digital intersection. Digital content is increasingly prevalence in our daily lives, and as such its effects reach deeply into our emotional well being, wrapping around our lives; it encompasses and extends our environment, from the public to the most personal space.

The relationship between individuals and their domestic technology is increasingly involved, some would argue pervasive. As we evolve many of our daily activities to include digital content, the importance individuals place on the objects and spaces, that have enabled these changes, become increasingly evident in how people spend their time, money and energy. In order to create useful and intuitive interaction with digital content it is essential for artists and designers to understand and explore the expected conventions users bring to these experiences.

With the increased use of technology in our daily lives, much of our time, energy and space are spent with objects that seemingly have no emotional significances or personal connection. We embrace these technological objects not because of their meaning but

of what they facilitate. Mundane items such as washing machines do not hold emotional value, but enable us to live comfortable lives without the need to spend large amounts of time on tedious manual chores.

"The most profound technologies are those that disappear. They weave themselves into the fabric of everyday like until they are indistinguishable from it."
M. Weiser (1991)

Figure 2. Home Router. The domestic router's abstract lightshow is a constant reminder of the permeability of our sacred domestic space.

The argument for more considerate technology (to start to blend or camouflage these objects into our domestic setting) seems more important now than ever. As designers find new innovative ways of freeing up our time from menial tasks, more objects, devices and technologies that enable this fill our lives and personal spaces.

This strange symbiosis means we increasingly populate our domestic environment with complex and technological objects. These technologies demand attention similar to the objects we choose with which

to express ourselves. They require maintenance, cleaning, monitoring and most importantly our space and time.

Our domestic landscape

The notion of expressing ourselves within the canvas of our domestic spaces is a deeply rooted practice, steeped in tradition and personal identity. It is an expression that in many ways fulfills a very basic human need to control and adapt our environment, but also key to defining and reinforcing our sense of place.

Figure 3. Personal Ideal. The objects we surround ourselves with in our domestic space speak of our sense of beauty, and connect us to our ideals and beliefs, be they notions of comfort and nostalgia or clarity and modernity.

Domestic space and the objects in which we surround ourselves are physical manifestations through which we express ideas, feelings, culture, beliefs and values; the ways in which these reflect upon us are in most cases conscious efforts to change or reinforce parts of our personalities that we identify with.

As more of our daily activities embrace digital content we find an increasing dislocated physical environment, where there was once order described through space and objects, we find a multitude of activities and ambiguity. Grounding our intangible virtual content via more meaningful and intuitive forms, offers the possibility to anchor the meaning and personal connection with information through physical processes and interactions.

The real world spaces we inhabit have evolved beyond their physical characteristics; technology has begun to

dissolve into our environment, where wires reached through the fabric of our built environment we now find ourselves immersed in WIFI. From clunky physical media to cloud storage, more and more of the physical elements of our digital footprint are decentralized; in many cases removed from our immediate environment.

Figure 4. USB Bowl. The ubiquitous cables that previously connected our devices, are increasingly unnecessary, and inevitably consigned out of sight to the 'drawer of junk' or bowl in this case, however these connections previously provided a physical and metaphorical link.

Without a tangible or physical presence in our personal landscape it becomes increasingly difficult to emotionally connect and relate to some of the most important aspects that we traditionally used to define *sense of self*. The act of attaching meaning to physical objects and the display of these *things* (be they invaluable heirlooms or everyday objects) are important, as they can become anchors to the intangible memories and emotions. Take photographs for instance, the convenience and flexibility of digital photography has now become a universal tool and we now take far more photos than ever before, but rarely

do we print (physically realize) these images.

The significance these images represent, memories of places, people, meaningful moments of our lives, rarely become physical, often consigned to reside purely in the digital domain. With this in mind I have begun to explore the relationship of digitized memories to our own neurological mass storage, through the design of a series of objects aimed at expressing the intangible digital content through more than simply their function.

Figure 5. Mona Lisa. The Mona Lisa on display at the Louvre, the increased use of digital photography as an aid for memory starts to describe our general acceptance that the myth of digital storage is an infallible, permanent and reliable augmentation of our memory.

A Pint of Cloud - The reality of our digital footprint

The manifestation of personal cloud storage through a metaphor for memory.

Computer memory has seen many incarnations, from magnetic, to optical and now flash storage, increasing in capacity and reducing in size, but perhaps more importantly becoming more reliable and less susceptible to damage or degradation. Our neurological equivalent sadly is not as easily updated or backed up. With diseases such as Alzheimer and Dementia's increasing exposure in media, issues such as the loss of identity and sense of self are at the forefront of western medicine and popular culture.

Figure 6. Pint of Cloud. A concept visual illustrating the metaphor for containing the ethereal within a geometric and tangible container.

Figure 7. Cloud Tether. The key elements of the project; an aesthetic and tactile response to the importance of personal digital storage.

In an effort to reinforce the familiarity and sense of safety through rituals and processes associated with employing physical objects to aid memory, I endeavor to explore what may help ground these intangible aspects in a physical process, by referring to established design conventions and user expectations.

Design interpretation

There are two main influences to this project that serve to highlight these concepts; the design of physical object that contains the information, and the process of accessing that information. Exploring these influences has directed the design of the project and has begun to allow me to explore this topic of memory, identity and the relationship to our increased dependence on external digital storage.

Firstly connections; in this instance it is the tangible linking of the storage to viewing device. The design of this serves the practical application but also aids to reinforce the concept of strong, reliable and trustworthy connections.

Figure 8. Cloud Icon. This image depicts cloud storage, somewhere out of reach, but still reliant on physical connections for data and power.

Figure 9. Cube Connection. Data and power connection of the storage device, the screw lock connection provides a satisfying and more reliable connection, avoiding damage to the storage device and its contents, as it cannot be accidentally disconnected.

All data and power connections are mediated through a substantial, weighty but familiar object, the power adapter. In this case the form takes its inspiration from the notion of a *power brick*. The casing made from Basswood describes a tactile yet sturdy material, softer and more humane than a normal plastic construction. The *brick*, as in popular vernacular, describes the general perception that this object maybe unwieldy and outdated, but more so it implies a sense of stability and reliability that we generally associate with heavy objects; that it is well constructed and can reliably serve its purpose.

Figure 10. USB Cable. A braided USB cable enables the user to access the device via a standardized and ubiquitous data connection.

Further cues from popular culture, such as braided cable shrouds and metal interconnectors also serve to reinforce the idea that this is a reliable and trustworthy device. I have employed an over engineered screw fit interconnector usually found in marine architecture and aviation design to reinforce this concept. The act of not only pushing together but

also the act of securing by screwing together the connections between the *brick* and the *cloud* (the storage device) make for a more secure, and consequently more satisfying interaction ritual. This is consciously intended to reassure the user, and reinforces the sense of a substantial and reliable connection.

Figure 11. Cube Cable. Connecting the device with a screw lock mating provides a sense of reassurance and added an additional layer of kinesthetic interaction, enabling the user to feel confident about the security of the connection and embedding a ritualistic tactile process.

The second component of the project is the design of the storage device. Aesthetics of the device and how the internal components function (or in some cases malfunction) could be a direct comparison to our own biological memory process. The design of the storage

device takes the form of a translucent acrylic cube, primitive, simple and uncluttered, the cube serves as a vessel to contain the complex array of components but also serves as a metaphor for the fragility of memory.

Figure 12. USB Flash. Flash drives were used to create the storage, they compartmentalize the content and provide visual cues if accessed.

The components used to build the mass storage device are a collection of outdated USB hubs and thumb drives, in an effort to reflect the way memories are grouped and interact in our psyches.

Figure 13. USB Array. The LED indicators change intensity and patterns of color to alter the aesthetics of the cube and inform the user.

The thumb drives have ubiquitous LED indicators, a sign that the device is active and functioning properly, but also serves to change the appearance of the cube as transient colors change and alter the appearance of the object as a direct consequence of different parts of the device and their associated information being accessed.

Figure 14. Cube Colors. The Cube changes color as the user views the data; color and meaning can be assigned by the user to aid recall.

The Cube is 88mm Square, roughly 1 Pint in volume; this is an analogy for the ethereal nature of cloud storage (rather than a measurement of digital storage) as if one was to condense a cloud of water vapor.

The choice of such a primitive form is intended to present a sense of order and clarity through its geometry. The stable, harmonious and unambiguous form is employed to represent the captured transient digital information within a container, not as a marketable product, but as an artistic representation of its contents.

As objects grow more complex in their abilities, there is a need to simplify their operation and our interaction, to allow users focus on the content rather than the particular form of delivery.

The idea of reinforcing the personal ideal with tangible objects and creating connections within our domestic space, be it either notions of comfort and nostalgia or clarity and modernity, is essential in grounding our sense of self in our familiar and personal space.

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Figure 4: USB Bowl. [Image] Author's own original work. (2016)

Figure 5: Mona Lisa. H2ase. (2012) MonaLisaAtLouvre2012.jpg [Image] Retrieved from <https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/1/13/MonaLisaAtLouvre2012.jpg>

Figure 6: Pint of Cloud. [Illustration] Author's own original work. (2016)

Figure 7: Cloud Tether. [Illustration] Author's own original work. (2016)

Figure 8: Cloud Icon. [Illustration] Author's own original work. (2016)

Figure 9: Cube Connection. [Image] Author's own original work. (2016)

Figure 10: USB Cable. [Image] Author's own original work. (2016)

Figure 11: Cube Cable. [Image] Author's own original work. (2016)

Figure 12: USB Flash. [Image] Author's own original work. (2016)

Figure 13: USB Array. [Image] Author's own original work. (2016)

Figure 14: Cube Color. [Illustration] Author's own original work. (2016)

Family Valuet: A digital allowance tool for both parent and child

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Abstract This paper discusses a design case built around the challenge to adapt the trend of increasingly digital payments to the topic of allowances. The paper introduces the concept and interaction design of *Family Valuet*: a tool that assists parents and children (age 6-12) in managing allowance. It consists of two mobile applications: one for parents and one for children. For children, *Family Valuet* provides a fun way to understand the concept of money and allows them to make better decisions on spending and saving. For parents, it offers a way to better financially guide their children.

Keywords Digital cash, Allowance, Financial education, Mobile design, Children

Introduction

In today's world the concept of money is rapidly changing. As the use of mobile banking and contactless payments is increasing, it gets easier for consumers to handle money digitally (Ortiz Jr., 2006; Hodgkinson, 2015). As a result fewer payments are made in cash (Snellman 2001; Heuts and Schijndel, 2011). Commissioned by the ABN AMRO Innovation Centre, this one month project examined the possibilities of adapting this recent trend to provide new and better services to the bank's customers.

An area affected by the decline of physical cash is that of allowances parents give to their children. As the amount of digital payments increases, it becomes less self-evident to give allowances in the form of cash. The focus of this paper is on creating a tool to enable both parents and children to handle allowances in a digital way.

Financial education

From a certain age on, most children receive an allowance from their parents. The Nibud¹ claims that a financial education is very important for children, as they will be confronted with managing money when they leave the parents' house. Children who learn to deal with money at a young age, are less likely to get

into financial or budgeting trouble when they are older (van der Schors, 2014).

Children start to recognize the differences between coins from the age of 6 (Zakgeld: hoeveel geef je?, 2013). Nibud states that this is a good age to start with giving an allowance. At this age most children prefer many less valuable coins over one coin of higher value as they think it is worth more (van der Schors, 2014). To make the child understand the value of the varying coins, Nibud advises parents to give a different combination of coins with the same total value each week. This helps children to better understand the value of each coin and how the different coins relate to each other. As children get older they develop a better sense of time which enables them to comprehend the idea of saving money.

On the topic of saving Nibud mentions the usefulness of a piggy bank (Zakgeld: hoeveel geef je?, 2013). Piggy banks are a fun and motivating way to help children save as they can see the amount of money growing.

1 Nationaal Instituut voor Budgetvoorlichting (National Institute for Family Finance Information) - <http://www.nibud.nl/>

Taking out the money every once in a while helps them to better understand the value of all the coins and to train their counting skills.

Early user studies

An early user study was conducted to establish an understanding on how parents, as potential users, currently teach their children to manage money. Six parents were interviewed, with children of different ages, from 1 up to 17 years old.

Most interviewees gave their children an allowance, starting from approximately the age of 5 and in the form of cash. Especially for children up to the age of 10, the goal of the parents was for the children to learn the different coins and bills and their values. They gave cash because they believed it was easier for the children to develop a feeling for handling physical than digital money. The interviewees pointed out that the children spend their allowance very differently. Some children are very eager to save money for a certain goal while others would spend their allowance immediately.

To conclude, we found that for younger children (5-12) parents tend to let them learn the value of money in a safe environment. Parents give the allowance in cash, help the child make some spending decisions and supervise or assist them in buying products. At an older age children are allowed to handle their allowance more independently, but the parents would still like to get insight in how the children spend their money.

Case: The design of a digital allowance tool

This design case focuses on children as they are a user group affected by the fact that cash is becoming increasingly digital. Specifically, the focus is on children of age 6-12. This range is chosen because from the age of 6 most children receive allowance and can recognize the different coins (Zakgeld: hoeveel geef je?, 2013). At the age of 12, children start high school and are able to manage a regular bank account.

Requirements

As discussed above, allowance is an important tool to make children financially aware. A digital allowance tool should thus not only facilitate saving and spending, but also to help the child understand the value of money. This means that apart from usability and functionality, pedagogical aspects need to be taken into account. Additionally, the design needs to be friendly and playful for children, as these factors support knowledge gains and attitude shifts, but without undermining the responsibilities of handling money (Gorana, 2010).

For parents, a digital allowance tool should make the process of giving allowance easier. It should also enable them to give guidance on handling the allowance but still let the children feel independent about handling their money.

Solution

Starting from the requirements and early user study, several design tools were employed to develop a solution. These include personas, a customer journey, task analysis, and use cases. The solution proposed is a digital allowance tool called *Family Valuet*. This tool consists of two applications: a parent and a child application.

The parent application is integrated as part of the current ABN AMRO mobile banking application. It provides a convenient way for parents to manage their children's allowance and/or budgets for other purposes. It allows them to transfer the allowance periodically and with a specific purpose if needed. Furthermore, the application offers parents insights into how their children are handling their money, which allows them to give guidance when needed.

The child application of *Family Valuet* provides a playful way to learn about the concept of money and allows children to make better decisions about spending or saving up their allowance. The application provides them with the possibility to create different 'piggy banks', each with their own savings goal. It also enables them to spend money in a safe way through the use of mobile payments. The final design of both applications can be seen in Figures 5, 6, and 7 (section 'Final design').

Prototype

The first prototype of both the parent and child application was drawn on paper (Figure 1). Afterwards the prototype designs were created in Photoshop (Figures 2 and 3), while Keynote was used to make the designs interactive.

Figure 1. Some of the sketches made for the child application.

Figure 2. Photoshop designs of the parent application prototype that were used for testing.

Figure 3. Photoshop designs of the child application prototype that were used for testing.

User testing

User testing was carried out for both application prototypes shown in Figures 2 and 3. Before carrying out usability tests, a functional test was done to guarantee that the flow was correct.

Parent usability test

Three participants of age 22, 24, and 59 joined the usability test of the parent application. The focus was on three aspects of usability: effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction (ISO, 1998). Due to time limitations it was not possible to find parents with young children. Therefore the testers were asked to imagine this. During the usability test, each tester was asked to carry out five tasks (Table 1). It was assumed that the testers could complete all tasks without problems.

Results

The testers scored high on effectiveness. All five tasks were completed (Table 1). However, all three testers had difficulties completing the task 'Find out how much money Anna still needs to buy a Barbie'. This was due to several reasons: one user could not read the white text on a grey background, while another one did not grasp the idea of the piggy banks.

Users did not score high on efficiency, as it took more time than expected to finish the tasks. Since it was

Table 1. The tasks and scores used to measure the effectiveness of the prototype. Mistakes indicates how many of the testers made a mistake. Completed indicates how many of the testers ultimately completed a task.

Task	Mistakes	Completed
Log in.	0/3	3/3
Transfer money to Anna.	0/3	3/3
Find out how much money Anna has in total in her bank account.	1/3	3/3
Find out how much money Anna still needs to buy a Barbie.	3/3	3/3
Add a child account.	0/3	3/3

their first time use of the application, this was not considered a problem.

The mean score of the ISO satisfaction test was 4.2 out of 5. This is a generally positive score, indicating that the users found the overall system quite satisfactory.

Child usability test

Four participants of age 7 and 9 joined the usability test of the child application (Figure 4). A more informal approach was used for the child application. The high fidelity prototype was designed already at this stage, but it was decided to test the application on paper by printing out the Photoshop designs. This way, it would be clear to the children that the application was still a prototype (Druin, et al., 1997).

The children were told what the application is used for and were asked to click on the button of their choice. They were asked to think out loud, so it became clear to what extent they understood the application. Six assumptions were defined before testing (Table 2).

Table 2. The assumptions and results of testing the child application (X = disproven, ✓ = confirmed, ? = unclear).

Assumption	Tester1 (age 9)	Tester2 (age 9)	Tester3 (age 7)	Tester4 (age 7)
They know what the euro sign notification means.	X	X	X	X
They know what the piggy banks mean.	✓	✓	X	X
They know what the wallet means.	X	✓	X	X
They understand the money matching game.	✓	✓	X	X
They understand how much money they still need to buy a barbie.	X	X	?	?
They understand the progress indicators.	X	X	?	?

Figure 4. The setup for testing the child application.

Results

Most of the assumptions were countered (Table 2). Overall, there was a clear distinction between the two ages (7 and 9), since the older children had a better understanding of the application. All testers had difficulties understanding certain symbols. It was expected that they understood progress bars to see how much money they still needed, but this was not the case. In addition, a wallet was expected to be a good symbol to indicate how much allowance they have, but this was not clear at all. Text was found to be more clear than these symbols.

Final design

The design of the parent application (Figure 5) is focused on fitting in as part of the existing ABN AMRO mobile application and provides a clear overview into the children's money management. To this end the design is presented as clean and pragmatic. The problems encountered during usability testing have been solved in the final design.

The final design of the child application (Figure 6) is colorful to appeal to children while staying true to the ABN AMRO color scheme.

A game was designed to learn children the value of different coins (Figure 7). Coins are used to help the child understand the (abstract) digital amounts. If the user has put the right amount of coins in the wallet, the system shows a win screen after which it returns to the home screen. There are several parameters in the game that can be altered over time to increase difficulty: 1) availability of certain coins, 2) order of coins presented in the interface, 3) starting amount of the wallet.

Several modifications were made after testing. The purple euro sign to notify the user of incoming money was replaced by text. In addition, the progress bars were replaced by a clear visualization of the money.

Figure 5. The final design for the parent application prototype adjusted after testing.

Figure 6. The final design for the child app prototype adjusted after testing.

Figure 7. The game to help the user learn the different values of coins.

Discussion and conclusion

This pictorial discussed the concept and interaction design process of Family Valuet, which was created as a tool for digital allowance and consists of two applications, one for parents and one for children.

Further testing is needed to determine the long term value of the application. This is due to several reasons. First of all, the final designs are not user tested yet. Secondly, the parent application was not tested by people with young children. They might react differently to the application than the current testers. Thirdly, the child application was tested by children of age 7 and 9, while the focus is on children from 6-12. How will a child of 11 react to the application?

For future work, it would be interesting to integrate multiple designs and games. Varying designs may contribute to the user experience as the age group of 6-12 is very diverse. Including more games could make the application more attractive to the diverse user group. Although there is still room for improvement, the interviewees and test subjects generally responded positively to *Family Valuet*.

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Nostalgia as inspiration for fashion design – Designing the present of future through nostalgia

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Abstract Nostalgia is a recurring theme throughout the creative process of many fashion designers (Mollow, 2004).

According to Tilburg, Sedikides & Wildschut (2015), nostalgia can particularly favour and encourage creativity. Thanks to their research on creativity and literature, based on a nostalgic daydream of the present and the future, they have come to the conclusion that nostalgia can be a very efficient tool to spur on a creative process.

But how does nostalgia fuel a creative approach in fashion design? How does the past merge with the present to formulate fashion's future?

This phenomenon will be explored by using nostalgia as a starting point for the creative process of three designers, as well as for three of the author's creative projects in fashion design: the 3D Tutu, the 3D dress and the mathDress.

This research aims to concretely demonstrate how nostalgia can be applied in the conception of a garment collection for fashion design students or professionals, and how to gain a deeper insight on this emotion without losing one's self in it, or feeling overwhelmed.

Keywords *Nostalgia, Inspiration, Fashion, Design, Creativity*

Introduction

How could we forget a garment that evokes a memory even more beautiful than the events that actually happened? How could we fail to be moved by a garment that evokes our collective imagination, through the weaving of its intended use and sheer physical aesthetic? By applying the postulate that nostalgia is a common human emotion, we can affirm that it reaches our passions and as such, colours each person's memories (Saint Augustin, trad. 1861). Should the emotion of "nostalgia" be included as a source of inspiration in creative curriculum in fashion design education?

Nostalgia, etymology, definition and semantics

The term "nostalgia" has Greek roots; it is actually made up of two combined words: *nostos*, "return", and the suffix – *algia* (*algos*), meaning "pain, suffering", and in its modern application means "a decline caused by the violent desire to return to one's home country".

So the term "nostalgia" conveys a feeling of sadness, caused by being at a great distance from one's native country. It also evokes a wish to return to the past, the melancholia of missing a thing, a state, a life that one has known or had, or that one has not known or had; much like an unsatisfied urge. (www.cntrl.fr)

Recently, writer Milan Kundera has utilised this word

in the sense of "the suffering of ignorance" in his novel entitled *Ignorance*, published in the year 2000: "You are far, and I do not know what you are becoming. My country is far, and I do not know what happens there." The writer goes on to explain that, according to its Greek etymology, "the term nostalgia therefore is a suffering, caused by the unquenchable desire to return (to your country)"; however, by observing the regionalisms of various European languages, many nuances can be observed in each language's semantics.¹

Nostalgia in fashion design – to convey a far-away (native) country, a by-gone era

Nostalgia is a recurring theme in the creative process of many fashion designers (Mollow, 2004). It seems obvious that nostalgia is a social phenomenon; clothing styles which imitate costumes of the past and popular films with nostalgic themes demonstrate that nostalgia can be experienced collectively. Davis (1979) explains that although nostalgia is a collective manifestation, it is also an emotion and that feeling

1 Milan Kundera further points out that because of its Greek roots, the majority of Europeans use the word "nostalgie"/"nostalgia", but states many other terms with roots in the local or national language bring a different semantic.

nostalgic is an individual experience. In order to demonstrate an advantage of nostalgia, he further explains that when we feel the threat of uncertainty, nostalgia can act as an umbrella by “reassuring us of past happiness and accomplishment and, since these still remain on deposit, as it were, in the bank of our memory, it simultaneously bestows upon us a certain current worth, however much current circumstances may obscure it or make it suspect.” (ibid)

Among the designers and *couturiers* whose creative spark was fuelled by nostalgia, Madeleine Vionnet² and Madame Grès³ both found tireless inspiration in an era neither of them had experienced: ancient Greece. Both of their signature styles were grounded in neo-classicism; one of the two used draped geometric shapes cut on the bias of the cloth, overtly inspired by formal elements of the Greek “peplos” (Kirke, 1998) while the other used tight, controlled pleats (*plis Grès*), mimicking antique architecture: silk was her marble and the woman’s living body, her column (Benaïm, 2003).

Later, Christian Lacroix fills countless notebooks where he finds inspiration for his Haute Couture collections. The books contain numerous collages that evoke nostalgic, inspirational moments captured in his hometown, as well as artistic influences. His very first *Diary of a Haute Couture collection* (Mauriès, 1996), which he painstakingly elaborated after a friend’s suggestion during the Spring/Summer 1994, clearly demonstrates his creative process through an accumulation of collages showing various places, eras, patterns and textures, juxtaposed on each page, and eventually, on each outfit. His first Haute Couture collection diary opened on the enigmatic image of ancient monuments standing in the city of Arles, in Provence. In every single one of his collections, Lacroix gives life to garments highlighting the history of Arles, his birthplace (ibid). Lacroix, while creating his collections, was introducing a vision of our collective imagination; a vision of an imagined past, based on a progressive thought process, a sort of return to our collective roots and dynamisms. It was neither a way of looking back, nor a leap into the future, but rather more of a spiralling effect that creates no repetition, but a forward motion. This move forward is a remembrance, an homage paid on a completely other level (Mafessoli, 2016). Having first studied in Art History⁴, Christian Lacroix launched his fashion house in 1987 and created a fascinating play of echoes and juxtaposition between the past and the present.

nuance: the Spanish say “anoranza”, and the Portuguese say “saudade”. [...] *Oftentimes, the term aims only to convey the sadness caused by the impossibility of returning to one’s native country. In French, one might say “mal du pays”, or “mal du chez-soi”. In English, the most widely used term is homesickness. In German, this translates to heimweh, and in Dutch heimvee. But the term often reduces such an all-encompassing notion to a spatial issue. [...] In Spanish, the word anoranza comes from the word anorar (“to have nostalgia”), which takes its root in the Catalan enyorar, a derivative of the Latin term “ignorare” (“not to know”). In the light of such etymology, nostalgia now seems more like the suffering born of ignorance. [...] Some languages seem to have a more difficult time expressing nostalgia: the French can only express it through a Greek-rooted substantive, as they have no verb for it. For instance, they can say “je m’ennuie de toi” (“I miss you”), but the word “s’ennuyer” (“to miss” someone/something) is weak, seems detached and lacking in gravitas for such a deep-seated emotion.” (Freely translated).

- 2 Practically unknown to the general public, Vionnet will own a fashion house from 1912 until 1939. She was an innovative business owner, who influenced the business world at the start of the 20th century. (Bissonnette, 2015) Hers was the largest fashion house of the between-wars era; at one point, she employed almost one thousand workers. (Demornex, 1990).
- 3 Alix Grès marked the fashion world from “the first half of the 1930, by consistently creating finely draped dresses inspired by ancient Greece and cut from silk jersey, by adopting a technique that allowed her to reduce the number of visible seams.” (Fukai, 2002) Initially drawn to the world of sculpture, she draped her styles directly on the bodies of her clients, and cut directly into the cloth, without a pattern. The Grès style evoked “Greek costumes, and were presented without any ornamentation, embroidery or accessories. This deliberate choice renders her styles classics, in the true sense of the term.” (Seeling, 2000).
- 4 Born in Arles in 1951, Christian Lacroix studied Art History at Université de Montpellier. Originally, Lacroix intended to become a museum curator – he became a couturier before coming back to his first love. His references to Arles were a recurring theme in his collections. In his creative process, Lacroix fills his notebooks, season after season, with references, collages, idea associations and drawings that help him create his next collection. (Mauriès, 1996).

Figure 1. Danseuse d'Herculanum, (museo Archeologico di Napoli), by Sailko (2016). Feminine costume – Dorian Peplos. Exemple of peplos wide wool rectangle draped: "the pleated top part can cover a first baggy effect formed by a belt." (Boucher, 1965) The cradle of civilisation, antique Greece inspired the designer through the principle of cloth being draped over the body, thus allowing a vast range of motion and enhancing its natural curves, without any trickery. (Kamitsis, 1996).

Figure 2. Robe Hiver 1920, Modèle 700, dit "Robe Quatre Mouchoirs" (Four handkerchief dress) (c.1918). Photo Les Arts décoratifs, Paris / Patrick Gries, All rights reserved, c.2009. Inspired by the "Greek peplos, a simple rectangle of fabric fitted to the body with ties at the shoulders and a knot at the waist, that falls in graceful and supple pleats." (Kamitsis, 1996).

Figure 3. Robe Hiver 1920, Modèle 700, dit "Robe Quatre Mouchoirs" (Four handkerchief dress) (c.1918) 1/4 scale replica of the dress made by Pao Lim (2016) and photo by the author, 2016. Inspired by the Greek peplos, the Four handkerchief dress is held together "at its corners on the shoulders and sewn vertically on the bias". (Golbin, 2009).

Figure 4. Robes du soir Grès en jersey de soie ou de viscose blanc (A/H 75-76, P/É 1975, P/É 1952, c.1962, P/É 1976, c.1956, P/É 1964), photo by the author, 2011. The inspiration for these dresses was Hellenistic statues; the pleating is cut and mounted on a base garment, which acts as a structure for the draped and pleated effect, as observed by the author in V&A Museum archives. During her six decades of creative output, Grès "worked obstinately on the same dress, always the same yet always different." (Saillard, Lécallier & Cotta, 2011).

Figure 5. The Temple of Olympian Zeus, Athens (174 BC – AD 132), photo by AlMare – Retouched work from Chrisfl, 2008 (“List of ancient Greek temples”, 2016). The essence of Alix Grès’ work is the French neo-classical style, where silk was used as marble and the woman’s body, as her living column. (Benaïm, 2003).

Figure 6. Anciens Monuments d'Arles en Provence, photo from Christian Lacroix: *The Diary of a Collection* by Patrick Mauries, Thames & Hudson Ltd., London, 1996. Born in Arles in 1951, Christian Lacroix studied Art History at Université de Montpellier. Originally, Lacroix intended to become a museum curator – instead, he became a couturier. His references to Arles were a recurring theme in his collections. (Mauriès, 1996).

Figure 7. An example of the numerous collages from Christian Lacroix (1993), photos from "Christian Lacroix: The Diary of a Collection by Patrick Mauriès, Thames & Hudson Ltd., London", 1996. In his creative process, Lacroix fills his notebooks, season after season, with collages of references, idea associations and drawings evoking nostalgic inspirational moments captured in various places, eras, patterns and textures that help him create his next collection. (Mauriès, 1996).

Figure 8. 3D Tutu (2014), co-creation with May-Li Khoe, Ben Cramer and the author, photo by Christine Butler, 2014. Exhibitions: Matter That Moves, gallery Hotel Particulier, 12th September 2014, Manhattan, NY, and Making Patterns, gallery space of Seaport Culture District, 24th July to 17th September 2015, Manhattan, NY.

Figure 9. 3D Dress – *Dynamism of a hand waving* (2015), by 3dTrio (with Sasha de Koninck, Leila Ligougne and the author), photo by Stephan Moskovic, 2016. This dress was inspired by Cristobal Balenciaga's sculptural drapings, between 1950 and 1960. Exhibitions: *Re-Making Patterns*, gallery space of Seaport Culture District, 10th to 17th September 2015, Manhattan, NY, and *World Maker Faire New York*, at NY Hall of Science, 26th & 27th September 2015, NY. The 3D dress was designed at Eyebeam and 3D printed at Shapeways.

Nostalgia as a starting point of a creative process in fashion design

According to Tilburg, Sedikides & Wildschut (2014), nostalgia can particularly favour and encourage creativity. Thanks to their research on creativity and literature, based on a nostalgic daydream of the present and the future, they have come to the conclusion that nostalgia can be a very efficient tool to spur on a creative process. This statement is observable in a number of fascinating fashion design examples through the 20th century, but also in my design work.

As a fashion designer, I have used nostalgia as a diving board to start various creative projects, namely two 3D printed co-creations and a bespoke dress.

In order to provide more context for this statement, the 3D Tutu was a first experimentation with 3D printing technology for all three collaborators. As we looked for the type of garment we would create, all three of us remembered our common experience of having studied dance in our childhood, and into early

Figure 10. *mathDress* (2015), organza silk squares dress and photo by the author, 2015. Model: Zola. An example of the algorithm created in Processing can be seen in the background, 2015.

adulthood. The desire to create a tutu stemmed from this common memory. Comparing a 200 year-old tradition to a 3D printing technique and material never before used to create a tutu became our project's leitmotiv.

In the case of the 3D dress, entitled *Dynamism of a hand waving*, the 3dTrio research group used references to Cristobal Balenciaga's sculptural draping and on jacquard textiles. The shape of the dress' hem is in fact the outline of a hand's profile. This shape refers to the value of hand-made craftsmanship in the world of fashion.

In addition, the jacquard loom invented by Joseph-Marie Jacquard in 1801 has often been referred to as the "ancestor of the computer", because of its use of perforated cards (Musée d'histoire de Lyon). 3dTrio aimed to pay homage to the traditional craftsmanship and methods employed in the world of fashion and textile, now being transferred to 3D technologies.

The *mathDress* is a wearable creation generated by an

algorithm programmed by the author in the Processing software. The juxtaposed silk squares echoes the see-through squares generated, their random colours and spin on themselves, as controlled by the user.

In this example, the starting point of the projects was a request by my daughter, who wanted me to create her high-school graduation dress; an important milestone in both our lives. Having visited an exhibition by Yohji Yamamoto, she gave me “carte blanche” to create a prom dress, which would enable me to express myself fully. The prospect of a “carte blanche” design was dizzying and made me want to take detours in order to gain a kind of distance; I therefore decided to program an algorithm in Processing.

Through the creation of the dress and by fitting sessions, I of course became aware of early memories of having watched my daughter grow up in the midst of my creations; but what probably surprised me the most, was that although I had often used draped silk squares throughout my creative work, the unconscious similarities with the work of Vionnet, which I had studied some twelve years previous, was quite striking. Not only is the “Four handkerchief dress” made of draped textile squares, hung on the bias, but the construction of the mathDress uses a similar assembling technique.⁵ The mathDress’ creative process is a concrete example of how the nostalgic state of mind can spur on creativity in fashion design, and produce quite unexpected results.

Nostalgia in the teaching of fashion design

Having studied fashion in three different schools and in various countries, I have observed that nostalgia isn’t an integral part of education in fashion design. However, I am convinced that the notion of nostalgia should be included in the creative curriculum. This is why, since last year, I have decided to add a nostalgia based project to my undergraduate classes in fashion design.

By allowing themselves to be consciously inspired by nostalgia through an association to a moment, a place, a person and/or emotion, the students are asked to develop a series of 5 t-shirts and conceptualise patterns and placement prints (abstract or figurative) that evoke their collection’s nostalgic spirit.

This five-week project is restricted time-wise, because after over eight years of teaching fashion design, I have noticed that students who choose sensitive and engaging subject matters have an easier time creating when a powerful emotion, such as nostalgia, acts as a bridge in their creative process.

Following this first analysis, I submit that in order to approach an emotion such as nostalgia, students should be asked to complete a relatively short project, of only a few weeks, which allows them to face and interpret the theme of nostalgia without stalling into a state of mind closer to melancholia. This way, they can add this tool to their creative treasure chest and it will in turn help to solidify, further and inspire their career as a fashion designer. According to numerous

researchers, nostalgia seems to have many other benefits on creative work and on people. This fascinating emotion pushes me to further study the subject matter in my next research projects.

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5 The assembly technique of the mathDress is similar to that of Vionnet, namely in her Four handkerchief dress, which consists in placing the fabric squares, sewing them from the outside of the garment (rather than on the inside, traditionally) and letting the edges fall naturally to create the draping effect. (Golbin, 2009).

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Have Balls, Get Tested: HIV prevention in African American MSM in Baltimore

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Abstract In partnership with the Baltimore City Health Department, The Center for Design Practice at the Maryland Institute College of Art developed strategies that engaged the HIV-positive African American MSM population in Baltimore City in order to collaboratively design ways to seek and maintain care, stay on their medication, and maintain safe practices to decrease the rate of transmission of HIV, syphilis and other STDs.

In Baltimore City, MSM are at significant risk of acquiring HIV and syphilis. According the Infectious Disease and Environmental Health Administration, there has recently been a resurgence in the proportion of newly reported HIV cases occurring in MSM in Baltimore, with a near doubling of this proportion from 15% to 30% in the last 5 years. In the BESURE study conducted in Baltimore City in 2004-2005, 40% of MSM who participated in the study were HIV-positive and 62% of HIV-positive individuals were unaware of their status.

Keywords *Health, Sex positive, Social design, Education*

HAVE BALLS. GET TESTED.

Getting yourself tested for HIV is the first step in taking responsibility for your sexual health and the health of your partners. BaltimoreStatusUpdate.com

An initiative of the Baltimore City Health Department.

Figure 1. Status Update transit poster featuring Ballroom Community member.

HAVE BALLS. GET TESTED.

Getting yourself tested for HIV is the first step in taking responsibility for your sexual health and the health of your partners. BaltimoreStatusUpdate.com

An initiative of the Baltimore City Health Department.

Figure 2. Status Update transit poster featuring Ballroom Community member.

HAVE BALLS. GET TESTED.

Getting yourself tested for HIV is the first step in taking responsibility for your sexual health and the health of your partners. BaltimoreStatusUpdate.com

An initiative of the Baltimore City Health Department.

Trebre Blahnik, House of Revlon

Figure 3. Status Update transit poster featuring Ballroom Community member.

HAVE BALLS. GET TESTED.

Getting yourself tested for HIV is the first step in taking responsibility for your sexual health and the health of your partners. BaltimoreStatusUpdate.com

An initiative of the Baltimore City Health Department.

Figure 4. Status Update transit poster featuring Ballroom Community member.

HAVE BALLS. GET TESTED.

Getting yourself tested for HIV is the first step in taking responsibility for your sexual health and the health of your partners. BaltimoreStatusUpdate.com

An initiative of the Baltimore City Health Department.

Figure 5. Status Update transit poster featuring Ballroom Community member.

HAVE BALLS. GET TESTED.

Getting yourself tested for HIV is the first step in taking responsibility for your sexual health and the health of your partners. BaltimoreStatusUpdate.com

An initiative of the Baltimore City Health Department.

Figure 6. Status Update transit poster featuring Ballroom Community member.

HAVE BALLS. GET TESTED.

Getting yourself tested for HIV is the first step in taking responsibility for your sexual health and the health of your partners. BaltimoreStatusUpdate.com

An initiative of the Baltimore City Health Department.

Figure 7. Status Update transit poster featuring Ballroom Community member.

HAVE BALLS. GET TESTED.

Getting yourself tested for HIV is the first step in taking responsibility for your sexual health and the health of your partners. BaltimoreStatusUpdate.com

An initiative of the Baltimore City Health Department.

Figure 8. Status Update transit poster featuring Ballroom Community member.

Have Balls, Get Tested is part of the ongoing citywide Status Update campaign which was originally developed to increase HIV testing among African American MSM (men who have sex with men). The campaign has recently expanded into a second phase which is a lifestyle magazine called Ball that is focused on continuation of care for those with HIV, enabling them to stay on their medication, and maintain safe sexual health practices to protect their partners and to decrease the rate of transmission of HIV, syphilis, and other STDs. Ball embeds a public health message within a fun, engaging sex positive publication that was developed specifically with and for the African American MSM community, and is fully funded by the Baltimore City Health Department. While there are many national campaigns focused on HIV testing and prevention, at the time of the Ball magazine project, there was only one campaign focused on continuation of care.

The primary audience for the Status Update campaign is the African American MSM Ballroom Community, which includes gay, queer and transgender individuals who self-identify as “triple-disenfranchised”. They’re black, they’re male, and they’re gay. Their sexual identity often leads to lack of access to traditional African American support networks such as family and church groups, and has resulted in the formation of non-traditional family support systems which manifest as “Houses” in the Ballroom community. The Ballroom Community has an intensively competitive focus, and holds frequent “Balls” which are events that feature performance, dance and competition, and this is rewarded by awarding trophies and awards, and ultimately gaining status within the ballroom community. Longtime performers hope to achieve the highly coveted status of Legend or Icon.

This project is an innovative partnership between the Baltimore City Health Department, the Center for Design Practice at the Maryland Institute College of Art, and the Baltimore City House Community, which is primarily composed of African American LGBTQ individuals. The project took place over multiple semesters, with a focus on building genuine and authentic trust between the student design team, the Health Department, and the Ballroom community. Community members were deeply involved throughout the entire project, helping develop campaign messaging and language, vetting design concepts, and participating in community and social events such as film screenings.

The interdisciplinary student team was composed of undergraduate and graduate design students as well as fine artists, and worked directly with the Ballroom community to develop messaging and design concepts. The team utilized a human-centered, process-based approach that had three phases: Research & Immersion, Ideation, and Pitch. Due to the nature of the project and the vulnerability of the audience, students were hand selected through a rigorous application process that required a high level of design experience and sophistication, as well as the ability to work in an empathic, supportive, collaborative and non-judgmental manner. All student designers

signed confidentiality agreements which protected project participants identities and personal information until the project was publicly launched.

Along with a faculty project manager, students led every phase of the project, from concept to publication, and included multiple focus groups with the audience, identifying and interviewing project participants, art direction, facilitation of all photo shoots, and production of the final magazine through press check and execution. The audience was involved from the name of the magazine up to sharing personal stories and being featured in the publication. This was groundbreaking on a number of levels, as even though members of the community speak openly about sexual practice, they are reluctant to share their HIV status with their peers.

Ball Magazine went to press in Fall 2015, and premiered at the 5th annual “Know Your Status” Free Ball. Participants and attendees of the event each received a free copy of the magazine, and were invited to share their stories and participate in the next issue.

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Baltimore City Health Department

Student Designers:

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Mindkeeper: Monitor your mental wellbeing

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Abstract In the Western world we tend to neglect our mental wellbeing. We ignore feelings of stress, anxiety or sadness until the point that these develop themselves into burnouts, depressions and other mental issues... *'We never saw coming...'*

After problems have escalated treatment is expensive, lengthy and bureaucratic. Treatment is also 'disease' oriented, reducing a person to a 'patient' and not focusing on possibilities.

As much as one out of every four westerners may develop a mental issue during their lifetimes. In many of these cases, escalation towards severe mental illness can be prevented by a greater awareness and basic care of ones own mental health. Very much like we are supposed to keep our bodies fit, thereby preventing to become obese or heart diseased.

Mindkeeper is a multidisciplinary collaborative design project that is doing just that: Psychologists, psychiatrics, patients, insurers, coders and designers have teamed-up to develop a digital tool that provides people agency regarding matters concerning their own mental health.

Mindkeeper will do that by coaching the user in seeking emotional fulfillment on the basis of the users emotional state and context. This emotional state is monitored by Mindkeeper thus building a personal mental health record. The data making up this record is visualized in a coherent and pleasing way providing the user with an idea of what is going on in ones mind. This results in a clear and attractive overview of an area that is usually shrouded in mysteries and folklore. The user empowered with this mental insight, may use Mindkeeper to connect with a community. Once connected, people can post queries, receive answers, compare ones situation with selected others and receiving and reviewing tips and tricks in getting or keeping oneself on track.

The basic idea is that Mindkeeper is aimed at relatively mental healthy people and that by using Mindkeeper, people remedy slight issues **themselves**, thereby **staying in control** and keeping the **responsibility of their own mental well being** in their own hands.

Keywords *Mental wellbeing, Emotional fulfillment, Emotion monitor, ESM, Mental health app, Groupness, Community, Big data, Data visualization*

Figure 1. Mindkeeper.

Figure 2. Several times a day the Mindkeeper monitor will ask users how they feel, what they do and who they are with.

Figure 3. The Mindkeeper control room, gives the user an overview of all the data. Not only their emotional state is being displayed as result, but also their location, activities and people there are with. Users are able to see their own data over time to learn about their personal development, or compare themselves with other users.

Figure 4. Each emotion in 'the control room' can be explored, allowing users to see their activity, location and company while being in this particular emotional state. The community (other users) is able to enrich these emotional states by sharing their personal experiences or solutions. Users are able to save insights from the community to their 'to do' list in order to actively engage in their emotional fulfillment.

Figure 5. The Mindkeeper 'to do' is an interactive list which shows all saved insights. The user will be encouraged to up-vote insights that helped them to elicit the intended emotional state, delete insights that did not, or add things that he/she believes will help reaching their emotional fulfillment. The user-ratings will help to determine relevance of each insight proposed by the community.

Figure 6. The Mindkeeper “vraagbaak” allows users to ask any question to the community.

Exploring alternative expressive qualities for the aging of plastics – The case of ‘timelapse’ experimental project

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Abstract In collaboration with the Italian design company Serralunga, this project was developed as a research on new expressive qualities for plastics. The goal was to convey a feeling of impermanence through the surface of plastics, thus reducing the perception of a timeless perfection. Among synthetic materials, plastics are characterized by an unnatural aging, which can occur in two ways. They can be immune to traces, resulting as unrealistic and ‘always-perfect’. Alternatively, they can crack, break, and fall, often degrading their aesthetic value. The inability to mature gracefully contributes to the overall association of plastic artifacts to cheap and disposable products. Thus, plastic artifacts are scarcely the targets of users’ affective attachment, ultimately shortening their lifespans. The point of departure of this project was then the possibility to make plastics grow traces of time and usage. The resulting concepts aim at increasing users’ emotional attachment to artifacts, linking our stories to theirs. By undertaking a collaborative process, the designer, together with company experts, explored different design directions, to achieve several outcomes that are depicted in this pictorial.

Keywords *Emotional durability, Aging, Traces, Imperfection, Materials*

Figure 1. The project deals with the use of traces for improving acceptability of plastic artifacts. The first step was to investigate the notion of traces, which we see as a relational concept and not only as a material property. Indeed, traces share the ability to link to a meaning that we attribute to it. Examples of traces are signs of our everyday interactions with products, like scratches or patina, but also errors of production. Nevertheless, products acquire a conscience of what happened to create them, or around them, or with them, thus registering our stories. The scheme in the picture represents the possible 'meanings' investigated in this project.

THE PROCESS

Figure 2. To develop concepts of new ageing qualities for plastics, we set up a collaborative process between the designer, some material experts, the art director and R&D experts, with the participation of the company chief. During a half-day workshop, the designer presented some possible directions as raw ideas to fuel the discussion. The participants then worked together to identify core-values and qualities of the material to express in the concepts. From these, they could define and develop several ideas of possible experimentation. Some of them were related to the notion of 'time patina', while other focused instead on the idea of 'uniqueness'. A first round of experimentation helped to challenge the alternatives and select only a few to develop, which were then refined and detailed. The main outcomes are presented in the next pages.

INGREDIENTS

1. DESIGNER + EXPERTS

2. IN-HOUSE DIRECT EXPERIMENTATION

3. PROTOTYPING LOOPS

Figure 3. Pictures from the first round of experimentation. The three main ingredients that contributed to this project's success were: 1) the collaborative process between the designer and the experts, mutually exchanging knowledge and generating new one; 2) the possibility to experiment with the material directly in-house, as Serralunga still offers the facilities to modify the plastic compounds; 3) iterative and quick loops of prototyping & conceptual design. Prototyping was optimized in its costs by testing the effect on small samples that were produced along with scheduled production, thus reducing the cost of operating machines and energy.

RESULTS // 1

time patina

BEFORE

AFTER

INTENTION:

create a patina of metal powder
to make the plastic change color
over time

PROBLEM IN REALIZATION:

powder during rotational molding
is taken towards the centre

SOLUTION:

special wax pastels were developed to
deposit the powder on the mould prior to
production. The wax holds for sufficient
time the powder onto the surface of the
mould. After few minutes, the wax slowly
melts, disappearing completely during the
production process.

A similar technique was used in previous
experimentation by Serralunga experts.
Discussing with them, the designer refined
and adopted it for the specific purpose of
letting the metal powder outside, while
being a part of the process itself.

Figure 4. The preferred direction to achieve a graceful aging for plastic involved the use of pure metal powder (such as copper, bronze) on the external surface of plastics. However, it was defined as a project goal to avoid solutions such as finishing treatments, and to achieve these results directly from rotational molding. This manufacturing process exploits rotational movement and centripetal forces to create volumetric, hollow products. The picture also narrates the solution developed to hold the metal powder on the surface of the product.

RESULTS // 2

uniqueness

INTENTION:

create 'always-different' products as a result of a controlled randomness in production process

1. natural pigments were used as additives. the resulting colors are always different

2. a serendipitous error: while experimenting on transparent plastic, we discovered that Polycarbonate reacts in contact with a TEFLON mould, creating bubbles in the material

3. other solutions were developed by Serralunga experts scattering leftovers and semi-processed material in the mould

Figure 5. Lastly, we narrated the main results achieved in the series 'uniqueness'. In this case, the project goal was to find techniques to produce 'always-different vases', in which traces result from production process.

Feedforward Toaster: Design mapping for expressive use

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Abstract This pictorial presents the design and design process of the Expressive Toaster, a research through design case that explores the mapping between the way the toaster is used and the way the bread is toasted. The Expressive Toaster is characterized by a textured cover that can be stroked to set the temperature as well as the duration of toasting. On the other hand, the texture enables the user to feel what the bread will become in terms of its crispiness. Some key insights taken from the iterative design process of the Expressive Toaster are elaborated in a visually annotated manner. With this work, we aim to provide practical design pointers for developing interaction mappings of expressive input to a delayed output over diverse modalities. We further intend to inspire design engineers to shift from function and menu based interfaces to expressive rich and other embodied mechanisms for interaction.

Keywords *Interaction design, Research through design, Expressive interaction, Toaster, Feedforward*

Figure 1. The Expressive Toaster as an experienceable prototype. The design is characterized by the lack of buttons, switches, knobs and so forth, to set the temperature and time. Instead, the Expressive Toaster can be set by stroking down the textured cover.

Introduction

Interfaces of products are often characterized by the application of buttons, menu structures, and labels giving access to functionalities. Over the past two decades, interaction design approaches such as experience design, affective interaction, tangible interaction, embodied interaction and so forth were

put forward to counterbalance this tradition by emphasizing the embodied skills of people (Dourish, 2001; Klemmer, Hartmann & Takayama, 2006; Harrison, Tatar & Sengers, 2007). In this countermovement, the aesthetics of interaction became an apparent focus for design research (see Djajadiningrat, Overbeeke & Wensveen, 2000; Löwgren & Stolterman, 2004).

In our work, we have the simple aim to “think beauty in interaction” (Djajadiningrat, Overbeeke & Wensveen, 2000) and we do so by focusing on designing tight couplings between input and output to achieve interactions that are perceived as intuitive, expressive rich and engaging (Wensveen, Djajadiningrat & Overbeeke, 2004). In our approach, we adopted the Interaction Frogger Framework that emphasizes on six aspects to couple (e.g., time, location, direction, modality, dynamics and expression). This design practical framework captures the essence of Gibsonian affordance and the reciprocal nature of our perception (Noë, 2004) in the useful concepts of feedback (i.e., the feed that says something about what you did) and feedforwards (the feed that will tell something about what you will do). By merging feedback and feedforward an *interactive materiality* (Stienstra, Bruns Alonso, Wensveen & Kuenen, 2012) can emerge. That is, by continuously mapping the input to the output, a feedback loop can start to function as feedforward. As such, people that engage in an interaction are enabled to real-time anticipate on their behavior. This mechanism is useful when mapping expressive input to expressive outputs. For example, the Affective Pen that captures stress data gives a real-time feedforward in the form of anti-movements. This closed loop in which stress data is mapped to anti-stress expressions in a sustained continuous expressive manner manages to lower the stress of the pen-fiddler (Bruns Alonso, Hummels, Keyson & Hekkert, 2013).

Objective

The aim of the Expressive Toaster was to design an alternative way of engaging with a toaster in which expression and the aesthetics of interaction are pivotal. We furthermore sought to overcome a delay between action and reaction as is the case in for example microwaves, alarm clocks, and toasters. A user can act and can consequently perceive feedback on its expressive action once the food is microwaved, the alarm rings or the toast is ready. However, the duration of the action is disabling an action-perception loop in which the feedback could start to function as feedforward (i.e., enable the user to grasp what the expressive output will be and adjust accordingly in the moment of interaction). Our ambition was to overcome this time discrepancy.

The Expressive Toaster

The design is characterized by a textured cover that can be stroked to set the temperature as well as the duration of toasting. On the other hand, the texture enables the user to feel what the bread will become regarding its crispiness. After the user places the bread in the toaster, the cover can be stroked from top to bottom; the slice will move down simultaneously.

Use scenarios

The way of stroking the Expressive Toaster and how this texture feels in this interaction is mapped to the way the bread will be toasted. That is, if the user strokes the cover gently, the texture feels smooth, and the bread moves down gently as well. Consequently, the toast will not be heated in a way that it will get hard and crispy. Rather, the bread will be toasted in a

way that the texture of the bread feels smooth as well.

In case, the user strokes the cover of the Expressive Toaster more roughly, the texture of the cover will leave a rough sensation while stroking. Furthermore, the bread will go down in this rougher manner as well. Consequently, the bread will be toasted as crispy as the sensation.

Use qualities

The toaster allows different kinds of stroking delivering differently (yet coherently) textured bread. With this design, the way of stroking is mapped to the texture of the bread. The open surface of the cover invites for different ways of interacting and exploration. We consider the toaster to allow for a rich repertoire of expressions. Bread can be toasted in the way users engage with the toaster.

The user will need to learn how to stroke the cover to get the matching toast. Each time the user feels the roughness on his or her fingertips and the actual bread coming out, the user will develop an own style of making the toast in the way he or she appreciates. Even though the bread cannot be toasted immediately, the textured cover provides a feed-forward to augments what the bread will become. In that sense, the action-perception loop, that is a characteristic of *interactive materiality*, that is difficult to accomplish due to the fact that the bread can not be toasted in the interaction, i.e., while the user can not perceive a direct feedback of how the bread will be as it needs a toasting process, the outcome can be sensed indirectly in the interaction by the smooth-roughness at the fingertips.

Design process

The Expressive Toaster was developed as bachelor graduation project Creative Technology at the University of Twente. In what follows, we first introduce the iterative design approach taken for the development of the Expressive Toaster. This is followed by a visually annotated elaboration on a few key activities and insights from the design process.

Approach

Within this 6-week project, the student took the highly iterative Reflective Transformative Design Process (Hummels & Frens, 2011) to develop an experienceable prototype. The taken approach aims to support the design of interactive intelligent systems, products, and related services and embraces values like openness, context- and person dependency, designerly-intuition, craftsmanship and development through reflection.

The student further focused the design process on activities that would support (a) behavior analysis, (b) synthesis in the form of a design mapping, and (c) detailing of the sensitivities in the interactive materiality. These foci, proved to be helpful in developing for the aesthetics of interaction when aiming at the development of artifacts with interactive materiality qualities (Stienstra, Bruns Alonso, Wensveen & Kuenen, 2012). The annotated visualizations of activities and key insights in what follows are a selection of a much more elaborated

process. The presented insights were developed in the design process that was highly iterative and as such can hardly be disconnected from each other. For the sake of readability, we have ordered them in connection to the foci. In the closing reflection, we briefly tie them back together, to highlight how these foci in the iterative process contributed to the design of the Expressive Toaster.

Behavior analysis, exploring current behaviors and possibilities for action

Figure 2. The first step in the design process of the Expressive Toaster was the removal of all buttons, sliders, labels, knobs and so forth. What remained, a box where two slices of bread could go into was used to explore different means of controlling. In particular, it pointed to the actual act of placing a slice of bread as an activity that is taken for granted in everyday use. This activity was further explored, i.e., different ways of entering to result in different settings.

Following Djajadiningrat, Overbeeke and Wensveen (2000), we decided to “Don’t think buttons and don’t think labels, think rich actions, expressiveness and identity”. Instead of focusing on Affirming and Appreciating the Current Behavior, we searched for behavior patterns that would emerge from interacting with a ‘clean-slatted’ toaster, i.e., a toaster free of digital interaction conventions such as buttons and labels.

Figure 3. The toaster was taken apart and extended with a motorized slider, servo, and automated switch. The motorized slider is used to move the bread up and down; the servo to control the rotary knob to set the temperature, and the switch to turn the toaster on and off. These parts, and thus the prototype are controlled by an Arduino.

Figure 4. The Expressive Toaster prototype used several inputs such as force sensing resistors, capacitive touch and an optical sensor (to measure the distance from the bottom of the toaster to the bread) to explore different means of setting the toaster's minutes (sliding the bread up and down) and temperature (actuating the rotary knob).

After it was decided to focus the interaction design on the way the bread enters the toaster and how it comes out toasted, the toaster was opened up to remotely control the functionalities that are typically controlled by the user turning knobs. The prototype was further extended with a variety of sensors to explore the implications of the movement behavior analysis.

Figure 5. While the prototype was opened up and extended with sensors to explore possible ways of input, the output possibilities were explored. Several pieces of bread were toasted to lay out the qualities of the slice that would result from the combinations of duration and temperature settings. From the left top to the right is an increase in temperature and from top to bottom is an increase in duration of toasting.

The key insight was that the act of toasting is not about the amount of minutes and a certain setting. Toasting is about the toastiness of the bread, the crispness, about how the butter melts, about the way the knife sounds.

Synthesis in the form of a design mapping

The second focus was aimed at mapping the particular quality of the toasters outcome, i.e., the toastiness rather than a number of minutes and temperature, to a fitting movement behavior opportunity. As indicated in Figure 4, several sensors were added to the toaster to explore a fitting match between the toastiness (of Figure 5) and an expressive input.

A relation was found in the expressive movement of entering the slice of bread and a possible toastiness. The basic assumption explored was that if a slice is entered rough, the slice will be toasted till it is rough. Different explorations were made with force sensing resistors, capacitive touch, and other sensors. In the process, it became apparent that a movement on itself could express a feeling that could be mapped to a specific toast quality. However, a feedback mechanism could support this. As such the textured cover was developed to create this inherent feedback of stroking

that would function as an augmented feedforward for the slice of bread.

In our process, it was key to capturing the crispness-sloppy-ness dimension of the bread in the aesthetics of interaction.

Figure 6. The downward movement of the hand while setting the toastiness was mapped to the downward movement of the slice of bread.

To emphasize the relation between expressively setting the toaster and the slice, we chose to map the movement behavior of the downward slide-movement to the movement of the stroking expression. In other words, if the person strokes the side slowly, the slice of bread would slide down slowly with the hand. An implementation of this mapping gave the users that validated the Expressive Toaster prototype in context, a feeling of being in control and the ability to express themselves.

Detailing of the sensitivities in the interactive materiality

Detailing for the Expressive Toaster was really about getting the feeling right. About mapping what kind of stroke (measured by capacitive sensors) over the textured cover, would result in a sensed roughness of the texture and a coherent toast.

Figure 7. Different cover textures were explored to map the stroke-sensation to the toastiness.

Details were explored by mapping the toast qualities to the texture and movement qualities. This was done in both the software, i.e., different scaling and gauging was applied and tested in relation to toast, and in the hardware, i.e., different kinds of textured covers were made to achieve a sensible mapping between stroke-sensation and toastiness. In essence, the toastiness exploration elaborated in Figure 5 was mapped back to the texture and software.

Reflections and discussion

In our design process, the input mechanism developed in the making process. The mapping of input to the output was not achieved at one go, but over countless iterations in both software, e.g., the Arduino code, and hardware, the textured cover. Not apparent from the description above, we had to move back and forth over the foci to eventually arrive at a final proposition. Our process diverted from the design process proposed for designing for interactive materiality in the first focus: analyzing current behavior. As we aimed to redesign a toaster and come with an alternative expressive rich solution, we chose to eliminate current interaction possibilities. This was a useful approach.

In the exploration that led to a definite mapping, a user was needed. We are the last to argue that there could be a mapping between stroke-expression and the expression of the toast that fits all, as we strongly believe that meaning emerges *in* interaction. Even though best mapped to the experience of the designer and a small group of 'validators', we do consider the simple downward movement to fit as an accurate indication of what the toast might turn out. Furthermore, we've seen that, through experimenting, people can develop their own style of stroking that fits their own preference of toast. This is not an exact

science in which people turn knobs; we believe it is a trained intuition that gets more and more refined in the interaction.

Concluding remarks

Many kitchen appliance innovations deliberately take away the user's skills from the making process. That is, by aiming for efficiency or reliability, designs aim to take away decision making and human handling by offering presets and reducing user-engagement to a simple press. This Expressive Toaster shows a different perspective that embraces the skills of people by allowing them to explore and express themselves. The user in its turn is rewarded for this engagement by a toast that follows this expression.

Through an iterative design process, that focuses on (a) behavior analysis, (b) synthesis in the form of a design mapping, and (c) detailing of the sensitivities in the *interactive materiality*, a toaster was made that invites for exploration and expression. The Expressive Toaster exemplifies that it is possible to map certain experience qualities over different modalities, i.e., the toastiness to the sense-of-toastiness and vice versa and that an augmented feedforward can be utilized to anticipate the actual toastiness. With this work, we hope to inspire design engineers to shift from function and menu based interfaces to expressive rich and other embodied mechanisms for interaction when developing supportive kitchen appliances. To us, food tastes better when it is prepared with care. Allow people to prepare with care, instead of giving them an easy preset.

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The T-probe: Advancing engagement with material concepts and sensory experiences

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Abstract This design case presents the synopsis of a practice-led PhD Design Research. The project was born within a contemporary field of design inquiry where designers are exploring novel materials and sensory concepts in response to advances in science and technology. Despite the human, societal, environmental, and potential commercial benefits, which underpin many of these design propositions, applying such ideas across science, industry and the market, proposes distinct challenges linked to human perception. This calls for intelligent and appropriate methods of introducing novel material concepts and related experience at the early stages of their development, which in turn, may inform and ensure the desirability and market viability of such concepts.

The aim of the research was to determine the value of using the T-shirt as a wearable probe – i.e. the T-probe – to advance engagement with, and understanding of, novel and challenging material concepts and sensory experiences.

Keywords *Materials, Perception, Sensory engagement, Probes, Design methods*

Introduction

Design probes

Probes are used in Science and Design as interventions to incite new ways of perceiving and interpreting reality, and to scope out opportunities for creative collaboration across both domains (Floryan Ivanova, 2015).

In this practice-led research project, the idea of a probe emerged as an approach to making novel and conceptual materials tangible, communicable and acceptable to users and consumers, alongside any further development processes in the chain of realisation.

The T-probe

A specific probe was required that would test response to material and sensory concepts that in some way engaged with the body. The probe had to be usable and wearable, simple and neutral, culturally familiar, yet versatile and customisable, and capable of operating within a range of social situations.

The 'humble' T-shirt, which is worn universally around the globe and has been successfully implemented as a powerful bridging mechanism for different purposes across a variety of demographics (Talbot, 2013), fulfilled the criteria of wearability and testability.

The potential of the T-shirt to engage audiences with novel materials concepts and related experience was tested via three discrete, but methodologically-linked research propositions:

Proposition (I) *Fungi materials for clothing* explored perception of mould as a potential medium for materials design and fabrication;

Proposition (II) *Fashion for deafblind people* studied how a fashion experience may be introduced to people with visual and auditory impairment;

Proposition (III) *Synthetic ingredients for fine fragrance* engaged consumer understanding of synthetic ingredients in perfumery.

The three propositions were selected based on common challenges associated with public perception and engagement. Each proposition considered how the design of a T-probe may advance understanding of the proposition. Stimuli such as fungi, textiles, and synthetic fragrance ingredients, were introduced in each case as catalysts in the design and creation of the T-probe.

Research Proposition (I): Fungi¹ materials for clothing

Research Proposition (I) sits comfortably within the field of materials design, where novel bio-based materials and fabrication mechanisms are being proposed and developed by designers in response to sustainability and wellbeing concerns (Antonelli, 2008; Braddock Clarke & Harris, 2012; Harris, 2013; Lee,

1 A group of organisms including mushrooms, toadstools, moulds, yeasts and lichens.

Figures 1-3. Research Proposition (I). Fabricating material forms from fungal mycelia² - early outcomes which explored the behaviour and properties of various species in response to traditional textiles, e.g. linen, silk and netting.

2005; Quinn, 2012; Ravensbourne, 2013; Royal College of Art, 2012). The proposition was born from a personal design interest in the potential use of fungi to fabricate textile-like materials.

As the concept of fabricating a textile from a fungus advanced in terms of materials research, the researcher began to consider how such a potentially useful, yet obscure material would be introduced to the high-street consumer as a piece of clothing to be worn in close contact with the human skin. Mould, to be converted into a durable material, would face the challenge of overturning its inherent negative associations with decay, disease and deterioration. Shifting this perception would be necessary in order for such a material to succeed in a market place that increasingly demands transparency of material sourcing, production, and heightened aesthetic awareness from consumers (Fletcher, 2008; Fletcher & Grose, 2012).

From this, the scope of the study expanded to create a bigger discussion about fungi in relation to design, fashion, textiles, and raw materials, by inviting potential end users to take part in the research and development stages for fungus-based artefacts.

Figure 4. Research Proposition (I). Fictional launch of a line of mouldy T-shirts.

2 The fine filamentous body of most fungi, except for yeasts.

A *Mould Perceptions* workshop was designed to explore perception of mould as a medium for inspiring materials design and fabrication. The aim of the workshop was to:

1. Elicit cognitive and sensory response to 'raw' stimuli;
2. Engage participants creatively to design a T-shirt for personal use by using fungi-based visual material;
3. Use the participant-designed T-shirts as probes within social settings, to elicit public reaction and response in relation to fungi-based garment designs.

The *Mould Perceptions* workshop created a platform for the researcher to pilot the T-shirt as a probe to testing consumer perception and engagement. When the research was being conducted in practice, the creative process showed active and imaginative engagement with mould-based media, and the ability to translate conceptual formulations into tangible designs.

Figure 5. Research Proposition (I). Participant 'raw' engagement with mould as a potential media for design. Image courtesy of Ezzidin Alwan.

Figure 6. Research Proposition (I). "Mouldy" T-shirt designs by research participants. The T-shirts were digitally-printed and handed to the participants to wear within a range of social situations for a three-month period, at their own will and in their own time.

Figures 7-9. Research Proposition (III). Deafblind participant s exploring a range of fabrics.

Research Proposition (II): Fashion for deafblind³ people

Research Proposition (II) was developed in partnership with *Sense*, the UK charity for the deafblind. *Sense* had an interest in extending the experiential awareness of their user group – people with visual and auditory impairment who want to go shopping for clothes, but are currently excluded from the high street fashion market. The researcher approached *Sense* with a view to employing the T-shirt as a probe to study the potential experience of fashion by deafblind people.

The proposition also referenced the compensation theory of sensory impairment (Lahtinen, Palmer, & Ojala, 2012), which states that the loss, or severe damage, of hearing and sight would lead to an enhanced role of touch and tactile memory. From this, the enhanced sense of touch developed by this user group could form the basis of a more sensitive engagement with fabrics, clothing, and inadvertently fashion.

A participatory workshop, i.e. *Sense in Textiles*, was designed, aimed at studying how deafblind people may be enabled to engage in a fashion experience. The workshop was set up at *Sense*'s Anne Wall Community Resource Centre (AWC), London⁴ (Sense, 2015). The study included 6 deafblind participants with varying degrees of visual and auditory impairment, who were supported by communication guides.

The Proposition used the T-shirt as a centrepiece for the study, by creating a framework for:

1. Eliciting participant interaction with textile materials for clothing;
2. Documenting the methods of engagement of deafblind people in a creative fashion experience.

- 3 A person is deafblind if they have a combined sight and hearing impairment that causes difficulties with communication, access to information and mobility (NHS Choices, 2014).
- 4 The Anne Wall Centre (currently TouchBase South East) is a day service that works with deafblind adults of all ages and individuals who have sensory impairments with additional learning and other associated disabilities (Sense, 2015).
- 5 Communication guides provide one-on-one care, support, and interpretation to the deafblind facility users during their daily activities.

Figures 10-15. Research Proposition (II). Deafblind participants creating their T-shirts with support from communication guides. Techniques included textile collage, image transfers, and direct painting / drawing onto the fabric.

The findings from the proposition suggested that the deafblind community may benefit and gain pleasure from a fully considered type of fashion experience. This invites deliberation by designers and other stakeholders, e.g. scientists and commercial brands, to consider research and development of methodologies, designs, products, and services for user groups such as this one.

A shorter term consideration for the immediate future would be to formulate and answer questions around the idea that design outcomes that emerge from designing for people with specific sensory requirements can have an impact on how fashion is perceived and consumed by the wider community.

Participant No. 1

Participant No. 2

Participant No. 3

Participant No. 4

Participant No. 5

Participant No. 6

Figures 16-21. Research Proposition (II). T-shirt designs created with deafblind research participants.

Research Proposition (III): Synthetic ingredients for fine fragrance

Research Proposition (III) was developed with the support of the global company *International Flavors & Fragrances (IFF)*. Initial conversations with the marketing team of the company were aimed at identifying an area of research interest within which the T-probe could be tested. *IFF* recognised that selling synthetic ingredients to their industry clients presented a challenge due to pertinent negative associations with the notion of 'synthetic'.

Synthetic fragrance ingredients are created as chemical molecules by perfumers in the laboratory, and are used in the perfume industry to add and enhance the range of natural ingredients, e.g. rose and lavender oils. The process of synthesising fragrance ingredients through chemical processes allows for technical, environmental and human factors to be integrated in the scent molecule while it is being created, thus providing opportunities for fragrance innovation, and a competitive edge to *IFF*'s clients, often global brands and fashion houses.

Despite the unique selling points of perfumers' synthetic creations, a challenge arises when relating such fragrance ingredients to industry clients, and in addition consumers. Generally, 'natural' is considered more desirable as it feels familiar and instinctively closer to human wellbeing. 'Synthetic' on the other hand, in this particular context, is viewed as 'chemical' and therefore inferior to natural ingredients.

In response to *IFF*'s brief, *The Scented Tee* was designed as a participatory workshop aimed at:

1. Advancing consumer understanding of synthetic fragrance ingredients;
2. Developing the T-shirt as a probe to evoke new thinking around olfactory design, materials, processes, development and marketing;
3. Employing participant-designed T-shirts as probes within social settings, to advance public awareness of the use synthetic fragrance ingredients in perfumery.

Figures 22-25. Research Proposition (III). Participants exploring fragrance ingredients and reporting their subjective cross-modal experience. Images courtesy of Ezzidin Alwan.

Figure 26. Research Proposition (III). Visual analysis of subjective colour-scent associations.

In Research Proposition (III), each participant selected one of the ten fragrance ingredients, to be printed as a molecular graphic on the front of the T-shirt. This design choice was considered best fit for testing the Research Proposition as the printed image was enigmatic (molecule and code) and engaging, to generate interest and discussion within social situations.

The T-shirts were produced and delivered to the participants with attached instructions about how to participate in engaging public reaction and feedback.

From the responses that were returned it was fitting to conclude that there was an overall positive public response, showing curiosity and engagement with the T-shirts. The following is an excerpt of some of the comments that were reported:

"I was asked what the molecule was on my shirt."

"I was able to explain that it was Cashmeran, and its use in perfumery."

"This surprised a few people who didn't realise 'chemicals' were used in perfumes."

"What is it? Does the t-shirt smell like that?"

Although there was less opportunity for individual creative and artistic expression in developing the T-shirts for Proposition (III), it emerged that participant response to the designed T-shirt probes was consistently positive. Therefore, the use of the T-shirt as a probe to elicit discussion regarding synthetic fragrance ingredients had value in providing research rigour to the study, while also paving the way for the employment of design methods and tools in olfactory design, development, and marketing.

In conclusion

The findings of the research inquiry demonstrated that the T-shirt is well accepted and engaged with, and serves as a probe both within, and outside of the designed research setting. The cultural familiarity, versatility, and accessibility of the T-shirt inspired communities and the researcher to explore, understand, communicate, reconsider, and evolve design propositions and market opportunities.

What clearly emerged to the author was that probes are a necessary addition and approach in design and innovation processes in testing, educating, and communicating new ideas, materials, products, technologies, and sensory experiences.

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Figure 27. Research Proposition (III). Selected T-shirt designs featuring the synthetic ingredients CASHMERAN, ISO E SUPER, BICYCLONONALACTONE, HEXALON, and FRUCTONE. Graphic design by George Newton.

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The Emo-T™ Global Wall: Design and emotion or emotion-led design?

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Abstract Human beings are emotional creatures. It's logical therefore that a major aspect of design thinking, planning and development is geared toward provoking emotion, speculation, reflection, and influencing choices and actions.

Rooted in the neuroscience of emotion, the Emo-T™ Global Wall is a project that flips the design-to-provoke-emotion concept, to emotion-inspired design. The aim is to stimulate, engage and activate the creative instinct whilst deliberately engaging with specific positive emotions.

Simple but effective in design and instruction, children and adults engage with emotions they would like to experience, understand, or cultivate and develop. Having conjured a positive emotion with deliberate intent, they design a T-shirt that becomes a practice in mindfulness-related emotion processing. A 28-day participation period is recommended.

It is our intention to build a global wall of a million Emo-Ts which will become a design portfolio that demonstrates the emotion-design loop and an artistic global platform for education and training of the future relating to development of personal emotion-architecture.

Keywords *Affective neuroscience, Connectomics, Mindfulness, Design provocation, Psychological capital*

Introduction

Synopsis

BY a simple process of designing a notional T-shirt every day for a 28-day period, individuals and groups develop a mindfulness mindset regarding their emotion state of being, and the ability to deliberately engage in an emotion that is experience-enhancing and of positive affect.

For the record

THE Emo-T™ Global Wall is an education and practice in cognitive appraisal¹ and positive emotion leading to overall positive affect.

THE term *positive affect* refers to the longer-term experience of an internal feeling-state of joy, interest, wellbeing, confidence, high self-esteem, and other similar mood states.

WHILST the psychology and neuroscience research communities work through the nitty-gritty of experiment design, participant variables, reliability, and all the other demands of disciplined lab work, the emerging research findings are consistent:

Frequent positive affect – i.e. being happy – engenders success across multiple life domains, including marriage, friendship, income, work performance, and health. (Lyubormirsky, King and Diener, 2005)

Birth of the Emo-T™ Global Wall

DOESN'T it stand to reason then, that developing the ability to feel positive is a life-enhancing experience?

And, if we value the emerging findings regarding the positive affect - life success correlation, shouldn't we be directing our focus toward the development of positive emotion in our being and responses?

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- 1 Appraisal theory posits that emotional responses to a situation are tied directly to interpretation of the situation as it unfolds. Cognitive appraisal refers to individual interpretation involving direct, immediate and intuitive evaluative frameworks to make sense of the external environment in relation to personal well-being. Personal appraisals reveal how people subjectively experience their environments and have strong correlates with specific emotions. (Yap and Tong, 2009).

Figures 1 & 2. Participants designing their Emo-Ts at a Sustainable Design workshop.

Figure 3. An emotion-experience training tool used in a group setting to stimulate and elicit specific positive emotions.

IT all begins with thinking about how we think and thinking about how we feel on a day-to-day basis.

IT's a sure bet that most mornings you give more thought to what you are going to wear and how you look rather than how you want to feel and what that conveys to others. How you feel on a moment-by-moment basis impacts on the neuro-connective biology of your brain, and is central to the project's vision for the development of a personal practice in cognitive appraisal and emotion regulation.

IN our neuroscience-meets-design brainstorm sessions, it became apparent that the everyday T-shirt is a wonderful, fun, relatable, and inclusive way to get people across different continents and demographics to feel connected and accompanied as they re-learn, or train for the first time in many cases, to cultivate and develop emotions on the positive affect spectrum, into a personal art form.

The Emo-T™ Global Wall

An Emotion Connectomics Project

Probes: probes are used in Science and Design as interventions to incite new ways of perceiving and interpreting reality, and to scope out opportunities for creative collaboration across both domains.

T-shirt connectomics: launching the T-shirt as a fun and interactive probe to promote active engagement with desirable emotions through which one wishes to experience life.

Neural bases of emotion: participants self-design their T-shirts based on conscious engagement with desired emotions.

Neural bases of perception: we are able to distinguish between very fine materials such as satin and silk, each of which involves different encoding strategies in the brain. Participants will engage with different textured materials in designing their T-shirts.

Emotion Connectomics: A connectome is a comprehensive map of connections between the neurons in a brain. The term *emotion connectomics* was inspired by the Human Connectome Project¹ and the emerging science of connectomics.

Our *Emo-T™ Global Wall* is a fun, participatory, and educational project to inspire the practice of exercising conscious emotional choices that feel good, wise, better, and beyond "typical" emotion responses that individuals and groups are seeking to change. Together, we can start reweighting, reconnecting, rewiring and regenerating neurons² one T-shirt at a time.

¹ The Human Connectome Project. Available at: <http://www.humanconnectomeproject.org/about/>
² The brain is naturally endowed with four mechanisms of connectome change: Reweighting is making changes in the strengths of synapses. Reconnection means creation and elimination of synapses. Rewiring is the creation and elimination of neural branches. Regeneration is the creation and elimination of neurons.

Figure 4. An awareness campaign utilising fabrics to demonstrate how emotions are experienced as texture in the brain (Bensmaia, 2008).

Here's how it works on the ground

OUR Emo-T™ wall-building occurs at schools, conferences, business meetings, in the privacy of your home, and any other setting in which people are eager to develop emotional antenna that enables them to deliberately access an emotion via intentional focus.

THE instructions are simple and clear and not overly prescriptive in appreciation of the inevitable diversity resulting from personal interpretation and emotion processing. Some applications that demonstrate how

the essence and integrity of the project purpose remains intact, whilst fulfilling the education and training needs of the specific participant group appear in the Design section of this presentation.

A kit containing T-shirt templates along with an assortment of colour pencils and pens is provided. Kits can also be ordered for specific events. Materials used in our kits vary from paper and cardboard cut-outs to softer materials like foam, for children.

Figure 5. Emo-T™ kits typically include T-shirt templates, an Emo-T™ Journal, and an assortment of pens, pencils, and other type of preferred artistic media.

Design 1:

Setting: Neuroscience workshop

Choose an emotion that feels good when it comes to mind, e.g. calm, happy, eager. Close your eyes if you prefer, and feel what that feels like. In that state of being, start to design your T-shirt. Have fun with it!

Figure 6. Participant design based on the experience of emotion "inspired".

Figure 8. Participant design based on the experience of emotion "love".

Figure 7. Participant design based on the experience of emotion "joy".

Figure 9. Participant design based on the experience of emotion "passion".

Design 2:

Setting: Public speaking training event
Choose a topic or a situation in your life that you'd like to feel or think differently about. For this exercise, you must be able to identify what emotion or emotions you typically associate with this topic. You should be able to do this in a few seconds. Don't spend more than a minute or two identifying your current emotion association.

Next, choose an emotion or several emotions that you would PREFER to associate / feel / be able to cultivate in relation to this topic. Close your eyes if you prefer, and feel what that emotion feels like. In that state of being, start to design your T-shirt. Have fun with it!

Figures 10-12. Participant design based on the experience of emotion "confident", having reported a previous emotion association of "chaotic"

Design 3:

Setting: At home 28-day Emo-T™ Journal
Background: Your 28-day Emo-T™ Journal is a thought-training exercise in self-awareness. It requires deliberate engagement in choosing and deciding to exercise your ability to direct your thoughts with awareness, and in alignment with, the kind of day you would like to experience on an emotional level.

Choosing emotion filters through which you would like to perceive the events and interactions in your life will determine how you feel and what you perceive on a moment-by-moment basis, daily, and then gradually, over your lifetime.

Designers and scientist often use probes² (Ivanova, 2016) when they want to introduce a new concept, create a new habit, or generate awareness about something specific. Your Emo-T™ Journal is one such design that will help you self-train and develop mastery at choosing thoughts and emotions with the deliberate intention of aligning with your life dreams and goals, or simply just going out into your day with a positive feeling mindset.

MY 28-DAY EMO-T™ JOURNAL

Instructions

Either the night before, or in the morning:

- 1) Close your eyes and silence your mind for 10-15 seconds. During this time you can pay attention to your breathing or some other stimuli like the sound of a clock ticking.
- 2) Ask yourself "What emotion would I like to consistently feel throughout the day?", e.g. relaxed, confident, happy.
- 3) Experience what your chosen emotion feels like viscerally for about 15 seconds or more.
- 4) Open your eyes and go to work on your T-shirt. Write, draw or colour – so long as your creative and designing impulses are inspired by positive emotion that feels good or better than a previous one. To ensure a smooth transition from feeling the emotion to expressing it, have your T-shirt template close to hand along with drawing materials.
- 5) Take a photograph of your creation, carry the hard copy with you, or start laying them out on your desk at work! Take a regular peek at your growing collection or recall the memory of a specific Emo-T™ on and off during the day, conjuring up or imagining what the emotion feels like.
- 6) At the end of the day when preparing for the next day's background emotion, fill out the simple journal questionnaire on the reverse side of the T-shirt template. Keeping an emotion journal is a good practice and essential in transitioning from a positive emotion state to a positive affect personality. Have fun!

Your T-shirt kit

Your 28-day Emo-T™ Journal including 28 T-shirt template sheets with a Feedback Sheet on the reverse (Instructions and A Sample Feedback Sheet are enclosed). Ensure you have adequate supply of pens, pencils, and other type of preferred artistic media.

Figure 13. A page from the 28-Day Emo-T™ home-training kit.

2 Probes are used in Science and Design as interventions to incite new ways of perceiving and interpreting reality, and to scope out opportunities for creative collaboration across both domains.

Feedback sheet

Name code: 070215.7

Day	Date	Chosen emotion	Time chosen. Please tick one.		Please tick the number of reminders during the day.			
			Previous night	Morning	1	2	3	More than 3
5	21.02.2015	appreciation		X				X

- Did you think that this exercise was helpful to remind you to direct your thoughts/emotions?
Yes
- Did you think that this exercise helped you to deliberately feel the emotion at specific times during the day? If yes, please provide an example(s).
I was feeling generally busy today but decided to feel appreciative of that state and allow my body to rest, rather than blame myself.
- Was the emotion you chose easy to practice?
Yes, also with people around me.
- If 'yes' to question 3, did it make a difference in your interactions or not?
The day felt easy.
- If 'no' to question 4, what difficulty did you experience?
/
- Did you feel this exercise was useful?
Yes

Figures 14 & 15. Emo-T™ research participant journal feedback. Participants are also encouraged to launch their creations into the world via social media, which then goes toward building an online 1,000,000 Emo-T™ Wall.

Hitting design provocation head-on

EMOTION and affect have implications for designers, design thinking, the design process, and the material, artefact or technology that requires designing (Immordino-Yang and Singh, 2011).

ADVANCES in affective neuroscience research over the past decade on emotion and social processing have uncovered that emotion and cognition are irrefutably

linked through the interplay between body and mind (Immordino-Yang and Singh, 2011).

THIS finding has important implications for the design of materials and technologies in teaching and learning domains because it suggests that emotion and learning are subjective processes involving intimate and intricate bottom-up and top-down biological processes and processing.

Figures 16 & 17. Interplay between mind and body as internal thoughts and feelings are translated into design through creative processing.

- 100 bn neurons
- 700 tr synapses
- Mapping neural activity
- Mapping anatomical organisation
- Mapping synaptic wiring

Prof Seung: pathways as streambed of consciousness
Natural – Normal Connectomics

5

Figure 18. Presentation of the neuroscientific basis of the Emo-T™ project based on Prof Seung's 2012 research leadership on the Human Connectome Project which began in 2011.

COUPLING the above with the growing body of evidence that firmly establishes a positive correlation between happiness and social indicators of success (Layous and Lyubomirsky 2014), and happiness and measured subjective wellbeing (Lyubormirsky, King, and Diener, 2005), results in a compelling case for designing education and training that incites and inspires toward self-mastery of personal emotion content and affect.

THE Emo-T™ is a budding project and campaign aimed at a worldwide coming-together of people who are eager to wake up every day and consciously choose the emotion-based filters through which they wish to perceive the events and the interactions that will ensue during their day. It is bringing worldwide awareness to the role of emotions in shifting perception and unfolding new personal, professional and global realities.

ISN'T it fascinating that after rationalising and logically arguing the pros and cons of a particular scenario in our lives at home or at work, it is emotional resonance with the things that we want that actually excite and inspire to new thought and action

"In conclusion, global campaigns and projects that are designed to inspire personal learning and emotion shifts that result in outcomes that feel fulfilling and uplifting have one thing in common – perceptions that create positive emotion buy-in that are in resonance with the feeling of the vision." (Flory, 2016)

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Figure 19–22. The beginnings of the EMO-T™ GLOBAL WALL.

Thinking Keeping: A practice-led research project which focuses on the act of opening or breaking in to product packaging

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Abstract Thinking Keeping is a creative, practice-based enquiry into the irreversible act of 'breaking in' to a sealed package. Breaking open a product's packaging structures the user's first experiences of owning the product, and reinforces perceptions of the product's newness, perfection and desirability. It is a pivotal stage in the emotional lifetime of a product.

Through creative methods we are subverting the experience of 'breaking the seal', by applying it to products that have already been owned and used. Our enquiry raises questions about the potential of packaging to overcome barriers to reuse, to help construct meaningful lasting relationships with products, and to challenge the desire for newness. We intend to expose contradictions in how consumers value, keep and destroy packaging. The research brings a new angle to research relating design to practices of keeping things and sustainable consumption (e.g. Chapman 2005, Fisher and Shipton 2010, Schifferstein et al 2008).

Design can play a key role in influencing consumers' relationships to their possessions, and designers are in a position to propose powerful ways of rethinking the relationship through creative, practice-based approaches. Our explorations are structured around sketching, prototyping, and data collection via exhibition. Working without the constraints of a commercial brief means that we can develop concepts that subvert expectations, and whose ambiguity prompts reflection and speculation.

Thinking Keeping is a collaboration between a product designer, a packaging designer, and a jewellery designer.

Keywords *Packaging design, Value, Emotion, Practice-based research, Reuse*

Project structure

Thinking Keeping is structured in 5 phases:

- Phase 1 Collection of packaging and related objects
- Phase 2 Collecting submissions of preloved objects
- Phase 3 Concept development
- Phase 4 Making and experimenting
- Phase 5 Exhibition inviting participation and discussion. Data collection.

The project is in progress, and phases 4 and 5 will be completed before the deadline for camera ready submissions on 1st May 2016.

Cultural context and related research

Our investigation is especially pertinent given the proliferation of unboxing videos on social media over the last decade. Unboxing videos record the act of taking a new product out of its packaging for the first time, to show the material reality of its features and

functions, undistorted by the product's marketing. The videos make a ceremony out of breaking into a sealed package, and invite an online audience to enjoy the material sensuality of the 'reveal'. The videos emphasise the anticipation and newness of the product, a little like opening a Christmas gift.

By focusing on re-packaging used goods, we relate our research to other projects exploring methods of encouraging consumers to embrace acquiring pre-used products. Post notably this includes the work carried out by Traid (Traid 2016), a charity actively working to challenge perceptions of second hand clothing, and ToTem (Speed and MacDonald, 2013), an academic project which included work with Oxfam to explore methods for transferring the narrative and meaning of a pre-owned product from one user to the next. A third example, from the commercial sector, is Poundland's "Replay" scheme, which refreshes, re-packages and re-sells pre-owned music discs (see Figure 1).

Our project also seeks to build on research in design for emotional durability, for example research carried out by Chapman (2005), Schifferstein and Zwarthuis-Pelgrim (2008), and Mugge et al (2010). These researchers have investigated the possibility of extending the emotional lifespans of products, by creating a strong and lasting relationship between the consumer and product. This has included considering the product's material wear as a record of its life, and factors that create lasting meaning in a product, such as memories of important occasions and people.

Phase 1: Collection of packaging and related objects

Having identified breaking open sealed packaging as the basis for our collaborative project, we collected a broad range of examples of packaging and other objects, in order to identify key themes. Themes arising included sacrificial opening, packaging as time capsule, contamination of pre-owned objects, ephemeral vs. durable, and actions such as smash, tear, snap, sensation of breaking through.

Figure 1. Poundland's "Replay" scheme recycles, refreshes and re-packages pre-owned music discs and re-sells to the buying public.

Figure 2. Selected inspirational examples of existing packaging and samples of our own work...

Phase 2: Pre-loved and packaged

In phase 2 we collected “preloved” objects from 9 people, inviting donations or loans of objects that had once been cherished. We invited the respondents to give us some background information on their objects, which became the starting point for our design responses. We explored possible packaging concepts for these objects through drawing and discussion, and through this activity we addressed the following:

- *Overcoming a sense of contamination, and challenging expectations of newness and perfection*
- *Transferring the story of the objects’ previous life to a new owner. Can the value be transferred, or new value created?*
- *Repackaging the object for another person, a new market, or for the original owner in order to help them rethink the product’s value*

Figure 3. Unboxing Sennheiser’s 100% recyclable cardboard packaging for their CX 300 ear bud headphones.

Figure 4. Preloved objects submitted by participants: Old trainers, a disposable hairbrush, a hat, a compass, a wedding ring from a previous marriage, a single earring, an iPhone, a drawing compass, and a set of engineers’ ellipse templates.

Figure 5. Pre-loved and packaged – initial design response in the form of concept generation using 2D techniques.

We selected one of the submitted objects as a basis for applying themes and ideas. This is a wedding ring from a past marriage, that the owner has struggled to pass on to friends or family. We selected the ring for several reasons. Of the objects we collected, it prompted the richest discussion between us. Other objects were very specific to certain lifestyles or careers and offered more limited possibilities. A wedding ring is an object widely recognised, whose meaning is understood. The ring once held deep emotional significance to its owner and presented a very particular barrier to reuse, which we identified as emotional contamination. The ring is a basis for exploring strong emotional barriers to acquiring a pre-loved object.

Figure 6. Selected object: a wedding ring from a previous marriage.

Phase 3: Concept development

We developed a series of concepts centered around the preloved wedding ring. Each one attempted to heighten the sense of acquisition or the “reveal” through various techniques, some of which are traditional (albeit exaggerated) packaging techniques whilst others are more experimental. We are exploring the idea that preloved objects carry with them an

inherent narrative, and each of these concepts attempts to reveal the story of the ring’s past in one way or another. We considered the ring’s story as a factor in its contamination. We considered exposing it through the opening of its package, and the packaging as a catalyst for overcoming the contamination and transferring the emotional value to a new owner.

Figure 7. Concepts identified for packaging the preloved wedding ring: From top left – The “long draw” box; A box within a box x 8; The specimen bag; The permanently locked box; A ring cast in plaster; A ring cast in clear resin; A ring presented in a charcoal block; The scratch card story attached to the ring.

Phase 4: Making and experimenting

We developed the concepts identified in phase 3 through material experimentation and prototyping.

Figure 8. Charcoal box – charcoal has cleansing properties and suggests the possibility of burning away old associations.

Figure 9. Box in a box X 8 – suspending the process of unveiling the ring and establishing a narrative.

Figure 10. Ring and a message in a bottle – there is a sense of magic associated with the ring in the bottle and the scroll placed through the ring contains a link to the past; A message sent from the previous owner to the new one invokes a delicious tension, what might the note reveal?

The images in Figure 11 show a range of further development of our preloved wedding ring packaging; the rationales behind these concepts are described below:

Group A) the “obscenely long draw” technique aims to create suspense through a highly exaggerated drawer technique. The concept is visually inspired by traditional wedding ring presentation boxes and utilises traditional carton board materials and assembly techniques.

Group B) the “exaggerated scale” box concept aims to diminish the value of the ring by the exaggerated scale of the presentation box, suggesting that the packaging has more value than the product it contains.

Group C) the “mirrored illusion” box concept uses optical illusion to play with the user’s perception of value; once the box is interfered with, the illusion of the floating box is irreversibly shattered; here we are inviting the user to consider the duality of this packaging product.

Group D) the “one-shot” box concept has a familiar “rip-strip” opening technique, very satisfying to perform and intentionally inviting but also irreversible resulting in a change of state. This change reflects the transition from new to “used” and resonates with the preloved wedding ring contained inside.

Group E) the “ring and message in a bottle” packaging concept playfully uses the message in a bottle construct as a

Group F) the “gaffer tape” box challenges the use of cheap, readily available materials to package high value objects, especially in the packaging of a preloved wedding ring.

Figure 11. 3D development and exploration through packaging techniques.

Group G) the “one in a hundred” box concept uses 100 presentation boxes that are identical in size and shape, only one contains the wedding ring; an intriguing visual impact and a sense of delayed gratification as the user hunts for the ring.

Group H) the “deconstructed” box concept contains all the component parts of a traditional ring presentation case. The unassembled parts are presented to the user who is invited to make up the box themselves. This act of engagement reinforces the emotional attachment to the gift box.

Phase 5: Exhibition Workshop no. 1

Workshop no.1 explored audience responses to opening a range of 9 prototype, playful ring boxes. It took place in Tamper café boardroom, Arundel Street, Sheffield on Friday 13 May 2016. It was structured as a small exhibition and was open to the public.

Participants included Tamper customers and Sheffield Hallam University community. We had approximately 20 visitors, whose interactions with the prototypes were recorded through film and photography. 15 people agreed to record semi structured interviews.

Figure 12. Exhibits and participants at Workshop No. 1

We intended the workshop to encourage active reflection on the act of opening packaging. Each prototype packaged an identical mass-produced brass ring, emulating a wedding ring. Some of the boxes employed existing packaging techniques but exaggerated or redeployed them, while others used unexpected materials, such as jelly or plaster. Opening the boxes was intended to be enjoyable and encouraged actions like ripping, smashing, and searching. We set out to explore our participants' emotional responses to the visual and material language of the prototypes, and to explore notions of contamination and value. The focus of the workshop was on the physical and emotional experience of opening, rather than on the wedding ring's narrative.

Participants were invited to open the sequence of boxes and then to rank their experiences in a semi structured interview. The interview analysis table (Figure 13) plots participants' responses to the following questions: Which package contains the most valuable ring? Which contains the least valuable? Which did you enjoy the most? Which did you least enjoy? Which package did you feel most driven to open? Which you would keep?

Further observations of participants' responses to the boxes include:

— *Several packages elicited responses that we expected. For example, some participants enjoyed experiencing the vacuum created by pulling open*

Interview analysis table

	Participant 1	2 (a couple)	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 (group of 4)	11
Eurohook display Cheapness - plastic bag. Rock bottom expectations. Spiral interesting - gives you a hint. Quality.											
Obelisk Enjoyed. Precious. Draws eye towards it. Pedestal. Most driven to open.											
High volume Most valuable, but annoying amount of space. Reminds of earring gift. Would keep. Lining nice to touch.											
Long Drawer Would keep. Higher level. Expected it to be in middle. Had to slide all the way.											
Russian Dolls Enjoyed. Quality and precision. Building up anticipation of quality.											
Stack No satisfaction. Didn't get any rings.											
Rip Virgin. Purity. Cheapness.											
Jelly Don't want to put hand in jelly.											
Plaster Most enjoyable / satisfying. Sense of achievement. Most valuable.											

KEY Most driven to open
 Would keep

Figure 13. Interview responses analysis table: Participants were invited to rank their experiences.

a perfectly fitting box and lid, and associated this with high quality. Eurohooks and blister packs were consistently associated with cheapness. However the analysis table shows some instances where the participant felt confusion about the value. The intricate spiral structure of one pack suggested high value to some participants, but this was challenged by the presence of the Eurohook. The unfamiliar combination of forms prompted participants to stop and reflect.

- *Some boxes successfully engaged the participant in seeking and finding, or even in determined pursuit of the ring. The highly physical act of breaking open the plaster prototypes was labour intensive, and encouraged participants to feel they had earned the ring and to keep it. Few people recognised the material and had no previous experience to prompt strong expectations. Some refined an opening technique as they went, while others commented on trying not to damage the ring. The 'russian doll' and stacking boxes also elicited determined seeking, and enjoyment for some (a 'pass the parcel' experience), but conversely other participants found them predictable and didn't feel motivated to finish opening them. (This could have been influenced by other boxes they encountered in the sequence.) Several participants developed personal strategies to opening some boxes, such as developing an efficient method of breaking away the plaster, or a team approach to opening a stack of boxes in sequence to search for the ring more effectively, or a method that differed to the one that was suggested by the visual language of the box (i.e. shaking the boxes methodically instead of opening each one).*
- *Some prototypes embodied clear visual language as to how they should be opened, such as the rip-seals. Others were more open and ambiguous and invited more varied responses (for example the jelly cubes containing suspended rings). Some felt the jelly packaging dirtied (contaminated) the ring and attempted to extract it cleanly. The 'long drawer' box subverted a familiar experience and elicited varied responses – one participant found his arms outstretched, with the ring in centre, unable to touch it. Another pushed rather than pulled, and accessed the ring with ease.*

Future work:

Workshop No.1 will be followed by additional workshops and will form the basis for more refined designing and making. Future workshops are likely to explore incorporating the ring's narrative into the packaging, and to apply the approaches to packaging we are developing to other products.

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Design for inclusion – How designers can help with organizational change

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Abstract There are more and more complex challenges in our society today. Requiring companies to constantly adapt and change. Because the challenges are too complex to solve within department or company boundaries we need to go beyond them. It is key for all stakeholders to come together on a challenge otherwise the change won't succeed. Or as Kotter puts it 'without motivation people won't help and the effort goes nowhere' Kotter (2012).

Designers have shown to be capable of bringing stakeholders together in co-design and co-creation. We believe they can also bring together stakeholders in organizational change projects and can even go beyond that in directing the change process itself. This design case is a first effort to explore how we can include all in an organizational change and what the role of a designer can be in this process.

Keywords *Organizational change, Visualizing, Designerly ways, Inclusion*

Introduction

There are more and more complex challenges in our society today. Requiring companies to constantly adapt and change. According to Brown, Harris & Russel (2010) we are not always able to deal with these challenges because of 1) their complexity; there's no single person, department or company that can solve them, 2) the compartmentalization of knowledge; experts have knowledge related to part of the problem, but the overview is missing and 3) the lack of communication between companies, departments, professionals and policy makers. Simply put, because the challenges are too complex to solve within department or company boundaries we need to go beyond them and work together. It is key for all stakeholders to come together and use their collective intelligence to work on a challenge otherwise the change won't succeed. Of course whether it is a departmental, divisional or organizational change, it is always individuals who are on the receiving end. They will ultimately cause the change to be a success or a failure (Cameron, Green 2015). Or as Kotter puts it 'without motivation people won't help and the effort goes nowhere' Kotter (2012).

Designers have shown to be capable of bringing stakeholders together in co-design and co-creation (Cross 2007). We believe designers can also bring together stakeholders in organizational change projects and can even go beyond that in directing the change process itself. Tim Brown recently named 'involving stakeholders' as the biggest challenge for designers today (Brown 2015). He even argued that the interventions that the designers designed to get a new service or product design integrated into the status quo is more critical to success than the design itself. Also, FastCompany named 'interventionist' as one of the future design roles. Which they described as:

experts in facilitating creative conversations (Fastcodesign,2016). All of which, we think, is part of a designer role to assist in organizational change. This design case is a first effort to explore how we can include all in an organizational change and what the role of a designer can be in this process.

When we talk about the role of the designers in organizational change, we do mean a specific part of the change effort. We think designers can be of great help right after the change effort has started up onto the point where there is enough momentum in the organization to drive the change effort themselves. (see Figure 2)

We use 'workshop design' and workshop(s) to work towards the momentum (see Figure 1)

To illustrate the role of designers in organizational change, we use an example of one workshop. Below some background information, to put the example into context.

Figure 1. Our specification of the role of designers in organizational change.

Figure 2. The position of the JAM process in the change process.

Building a new IC in a children's hospital (also known as the department merger)

In one of the children's hospitals in the Netherlands two wards are going to be transformed into one new-build state of the art - ward that revolves more around the patient and its family than the medical technology. This transformation is part of a change effort that is needed to bring the hospital around to a new philosophy. Extensive research has been done by the hospital and all the insights are collected. Yet the hospital team entrusted with the task of leading this change struggles to transform these insights into a inspirational vision for the new ward supported by all employees. Also, since the research has taken quite some time most employees are skeptical and do not believe the change is coming. All the research happened before our involvement. We were asked to design a workshop that would bring back employee moral and give them a voice in the change effort.

Figure 3. The role of the designers in this workshop and how they made sure everyone was included in the workshop.

When we start an assignment, we start with the communication model above. We look at the target group and intended effect (in this case; bring back employee moral and give them a voice in the change effort) and derive a medium from there (in this case; a workshop). On the next pages you will find a visualization on the workshop design, the workshop itself including the role of the designers and the workshop tools and the momentum. The design case will conclude with a reflection on the workshop.

WORKSHOP DESIGN

WORKSHOP MATERIAL

PROGRAM

The workshop program is the most important design we make to ensure the intended effect. We combine content exercises with energy exercises to keep the flow of energy right during the workshop.

The workshop material supports the program and makes it possible for the participants to build on workshop results together. In this workshop we used a single template that held all the results of the workshop and some inspiration material that we derived from previous research.

EFFECT

While we're doing the workshop, the intended effect is always leading. This means that at times we have to discard the workshop program and improvise on the spot.

INVITATION

Because one of the intended effects of the workshop was 'bring back employee moral', the tone of the workshop was important. We choose an honest, but positive tone that we set with the invitation sent to all.

SENSITIZING

For the same reason it was important to show the employees that we would move past previous efforts in our workshop. We did this with a sensitizing exercise.

Figure 4. The workshop design.

Due to the different roles we take on as designers during a workshop we are always with two designers per group.

In this workshop the biggest challenge was to get all employees back on board of the change effort and let them be part of the designing process. Therefore it was important that the designer was very aware of all the employees in his or her workshopgroup. Everyone mattered.

There are many design tools, but our agency has chosen visualizing as it main design method. It's what we are experts in. So during the workshop, the designers were also visualizing and using visualizing as a design method.

To facilitate an equal conversation between all the stakeholders a facilitator moderates. During the workshop all designers facilitated their workshop.

When there are different stakeholders at the table there are also different styles of communication and different levels of communicating. It is the designers job to facilitate the conversation and translate between the different stakeholders. In our case, we use visualizations to clarify the different points of view.

We design the process of the workshop on beforehand to create the best possible outcome. However, facilitating the conversation can take a different turn during the workshop. Therefore the designer needs to be able to change the process of the workshop during the workshop if that is necessary to get a good outcome. We believe that all elements of the answer to the challenge faced within the group need to come from the group itself to create a shared solution. However, when necessary the designer also is an instigator in the group to get the creativity going.

Figure 5. The role of the designers in this workshop and how they made sure everyone was included in the workshop.

We find that the best way to get different stakeholders aligned is to get them talking together and facilitate the conversation. Therefore all groups are mixed with different stakeholders and we facilitate that all have room to speak and share their interests. We create room for all to give their opinion but also try to connect these opinions and build upon each other. We do this by visualizing.

INTERACTION

WORKSHOP TOOLS

VISUALIZING

Our design methodology involves visualizing. It is what differs us from other design agencies. Of course there are many other tools, but we believe visualizing has the power to put intangible discussions to paper.

This is a key element in aligning stakeholders. All stakeholders can build on each other, because visualizing the discussion makes it tangible and visible.

PREPARATION

Our best workshop tool is the preparation of the workshop. With the preparation we gain better insight into the stakeholders and their interests. We design a workshop plan and materials to support the flow and the direction of the workshop.

Figure 6. The materials we used in the workshop.

Figure 7. An impression of the workshop.

MOMENTUM

“ The funny thing was that everybody was very interested in someone else's story ”

“ You get to know each other in a different way ”

“ You try to combine your own story with that of others and so actually achieving a joint plan. ”

“ You give us a voice to speak. ”

“ Drawing is a very nice way Thoughts are put on paper so you can start sharing thoughts. ”

“ Main result to me was to give employees a voice in the process ”

“ We basically practiced a different way of working together multi-disciplinary and that was very nice. ”

“ Sometimes they asked me explicitly, how do you feel about this? That way you highlighted all the different angles ”

“ The main result is that we worked together in a different way to look at our shared future ”

We are taken seriously and our wishes and expectations are put down and taken into account.

Figure 8. An impression of the momentum generated in the form of quotes from employees who participated in the workshop.

Reflection

Workshop Design

Extra time to frame the workshop

One of our own key challenges when we get an organizational change challenge is to create room for design in the change process. When we were first contacted by the hospital they gave us one hour to facilitate the making of an inspirational vision. Which is definitely not enough time if you want all employees involved in the making of the vision. What we encounter is also reflected in literature: quite often change is seen as an event and not a process. It takes time and effort to convince people otherwise.

For our workshop the preparation and making of materials was key. It was what made us able to facilitate the conversation between a large group of employees. But convincing the hospital of this necessity took extra time and effort.

Workshop

Tools that help to facilitate large groups

Over the years we discovered that the best groups size to work with visualization is about 6-8. A larger group will be hard to facilitate visually. The collective building is also harder with a larger group. Because one of our goals of the workshop was giving all employees a stage to give their opinion on the new IC, we mixed individual exercises with group exercises. We noticed that at the beginning of the workshop it feels more natural to do more individual exercises than group exercises. This shifts towards the end of the workshop.

Visualizing works disarming & levels the playing field

At the workshop we had employees from different departments and different levels at the table. Hospitals being very hierarchical, we knew we had to do something to facilitate the equality of group members. We therefore did several (unrelated) drawing exercises during the workshop. With these exercises we got everyone out of their comfortzone and clear the playing field.

Designers

In this workshop, the role of the designers was crucial to the success of the workshop. Therefore all designers practiced the workshop on beforehand.

A sense of pride

After the workshops we noticed a sense of pride from all teams. They were surprised by their accomplishments during the workshop and their team effort. We think it generated from two different things: the tangible result and one of the specific exercises.

Because every team had a designer, they all build a visualization of their dream IC. Seeing this result build during the workshop enforced their enthusiasm and teamwork. One of the exercises focused specifically on the new (animal) name of the ward. Every team had to come up with a new name. This struck a nerve with the participants. According to the

Figure 9. Rehearsing the workshop.

interviews we did, the friendly competition went on for weeks after the workshop and the new name became a symbol for the new IC ward.

Momentum & energy

With a workshop with all employees, you build momentum. Momentum for the change effort. You ask them to participate so the change effort becomes part of them as well. From the interviews we concluded that we succeeded in building this first momentum. Employees felt their stories had been heard and they had connected with different team members.

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Recovery from psychosis – Embedding therapy in the heart of everyday life

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Abstract 'Recovery from psychosis through design' is a design project based on a close collaboration between designers, mental health care professionals, and people with lived experience of psychosis. The resulting three interventions illustrate how healthcare can move away from the 'old' medical models in which the user is put in a passive position. Instead the project shows how designers can create tools that trigger new or adaptive behaviour, tools that enable users to deal with mental health problems in their day-to-day lives, and tools that empower people. The interventions demonstrate how mental healthcare can shift from an emphasis on relieving symptoms to a focus on enabling people in achieving a meaningful life.

Keywords Mental health, Wellbeing, eHealth, Reframing, Social design

Figure 1. De 'Aanpakker' (meaning both 'receiver' and someone who is 'very proactive' in Dutch) is a service for people who suffer from severe mental illness and as a result find it difficult to participate in society. It denotes a role for individuals that are usually at home during the daytime: when packages are delivered for neighbours who are not at home, these packages will be delivered to the Aanpakker.

Figure 2. The small sticker next to your doorbell indicates that you are willing to receive packages for you neighbours. With the sticker comes a booklet with instructions (e.g. “what to do when your neighbour does not come to pick up the package?”).

Figure 3. People who hear voices can have this experience every day, some people almost continuously. These voices can be very negative and are often linked to negative life experiences (e.g. neglected or abuse). People who seriously suffer from negative voices often experience a lack of control over these experiences and withdraw out of fear or confusion. Temstem is a smartphone application developed to counteract this detrimental vicious cycle. Temstem gives the user control over the negative voices and in that way enables the user to keep participating in common daily activities. Temstem offers exercises that encourage the user to actively grow stronger in their relationship to the voices and to enhance self-esteem.

Figure 4. Temstem is based on three working principles:

1. By playing a word game, one activates the language production areas in the brain. This same area becomes active when 'hearing voices'. Playing the game thereby overrules hearing voices in most individuals, offering a way to take control over the voices.
2. Actively recalling a moment the voices were imposingly present, while using your working memory for a different task at the same time (playing a game), causes an overload: the working memory has difficulties in performing this dual task. The working memory is not capable of keeping the memory intact, as a result the memory becomes less vivid and causes less emotional distress.
3. From level 3 onwards, the user is guided to actively strengthen him- or herself in relation to the voices. The user is asked what impact the voices cause and to what misconception of oneself this leads. Temstem subsequently elicits contrasting feelings by developing personal rewards. For instance, some users feel worthless due to the voices, while others feel in danger. Using Temstem counteracts these feelings to activate feelings of worthiness and safety respectively.

Figure 5. Project Network, the third intervention, is a smartphone application designed to help people maintain their social network while struggling with or recovering from, a period of mental instability (e.g. psychosis). A period of mental instability directly affects the relationships you have with family and friends yet social interaction is a very important factor in recovery. Project Network aims to motivate people to increase the frequency of contact with family and friends by setting goals and to be more involved with the lives of others.

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“Heb je volgende week zin om iets leuks te doen?”

“Heb je zin om een kopje koffie te drinken?”

Figure 6. Project Network also includes a set of tools for the mental health care professional to integrate the application in therapy sessions.

Figure 7. All three projects were the result of an extensive design research process. In a one-month pilot the concepts were tested through experiential prototypes. We monitored the mechanisms we wanted to affect, and after the pilot we could test whether we were indeed successful in addressing these mechanisms. Other forms of user research were conducted in various stages of the projects.

Beings of frequency. In-progress graduation project in fashion design

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Abstract “Beings of Frequency” is a bachelor graduation project, currently being developed in the form of a collection in fashion design. In the collection, parallels are being laid between the seven musical notes, the seven colours of the rainbow and the the seven main energy centers of the human body, the so called *chakra*’s.

Before seeing the collection, each visitor will get the chance to scan their *chakra* status via a GDV scan developed by Dr. Korotkov, PhD and according to that, a sound will be designed containing mainly the notes that are ought to resonate with their “weaker” *chakras*.

While the music is playing, by use of incorporated micro-processors, mini-microphones and coloured LEDs, the collection will give the viewer a real-time sound & light therapy which is believed to charge the energy of the corresponding *chakra*’s; operating as a resonant, interactive mechanism. The collection consists out of seven outfits, each representing one of the *chakras*.

Keywords *Fashion, Chakra, Colour, Sound, Interaction*

Introduction

Some time ago, I co-incidentally happened to take part in a Tibetan singing bowl¹ session. For the first time, I was not hearing music with my ears only, but was experiencing it as a vibration throughout my entire body. This outstanding experience left a deep impression on me. It made me wonder about how frequencies resonate with the body and it had become the starting point of my graduation project in fashion design. I tried to imagine for one moment: if I could see sound, what shape and colour would it then be?

In this writing, I will first elaborate on what sound actually is, on how it relates to colour and to the human body. This will form the core of the concept and will then be translated into ingredients for an interactive womenswear collection “Beings of Frequency”, further referred as The Collection.

The shape of sound

Sound vibration is so subtle, that it cannot be perceived by the human eyes. However, it is a delicate, perfect balance between frequencies that keeps us alive and forms the basis of all the natural cycles that we see around us.

There is a common misconception of what sound really is. It is believed, that sound is a wave and it ‘wiggles’ through the air from one point to the other just like that. Sound researcher, Professor John Stuart Reid (2009), has done deep studies in the shape of sound and states that sound can rather be described as a rapidly expanding bubble, having the ‘sonic event’ in the middle of it (for example from vibrating vocal cords of a human). Starting at that core, different densities of air are created by vibration and travel in all directions at the same time creating a sphere-like

shape.

Sound can only be made visible to the human eye when exposed to matter. The act of making sound visible is called Cymatics². Every sound creates a unique geometrical structure in air densities from the core outwards, looking very much like a mandala³ if you would slice the sonic bubble in half (Figure 1). Reid has developed a special scientific device, called the CymaScope. With help of a digital camera, the patterns are captured that appear in ultra-pure water that is exposed to sound vibrations. This sound visualization is called a Cyma Glyph and is used as the aesthetic base of The Collection and is interpreted and applied in the clothing in various ways and scales (Figure 2-6).

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- 1 A musical instrument made of metal, dating back from the pre-Buddhist Tibetan Bon culture. It is a type of bell that is rather placed in a standing position, and is played either by rubbing a mallet around the rim or striking the side of the bowl with the mallet.
 - 2 The term is invented by the Swiss scientist Hans Jenny (1904-1972), addressing the study of visible effects of sound and vibration, especially on the visual display of sound in matter. The name derives from Greek ‘kuma’ meaning ‘billow’ or ‘wave’ which has to do with the periodic vibrations inside the ‘sound bubble’.
 - 3 The meaning of mandala comes from Sanskrit meaning “circle.” Even though it may be dominated by squares or triangles, a mandala has a concentric structure. Mandalas offer balancing visual elements, symbolizing unity and harmony.

Figure 1. A Cyma Glyph. The aesthetic base of the collection is a photo of an interference pattern seen in water, when exposed to musical (sound) vibrations. Picture credits: John Stuart Reid.

Figure 2. A personal interpretation of the mandala-shaped Cyma Glyph, laser cut in coated jersey for draping experiments in small scale (45 cm height).

Figure 3. The small scale Cyma Glyph laser cut in ultra-thin polyester organza fabric for placement experiments on a full scale mannequin.

Figure 4. Cyma Glyph draped on a 1/5 scale mannequin combined with another material, later to be enlarged and developed as a full-scale outfit, covering the entire body with a single Cyma Glyph.

Figure 5. Cyma Glyph half-way cut in transparent Perspex. This way, with the right angle of light, cutting lines absorb the light and transport it, looking as if the image is emitting light by itself. Several hundred of these Perspex pieces (4 cm height) are connected creating a new, drapable material for the collection.

Seeing these images and knowing that the human body consists for 60 to 70 percent out of water, it not hard to imagine what a huge effect sound vibration has for the reactions inside the body. This makes a direct link to the basic principles of alternative medicine, for instance, healing methods with sound therapy.

How does sound therapy work?

Each organism has its own vibratory rate. Every object in the universe has its own unique resonant frequency. Together they make up a composite frequency like the instruments of an orchestra. When one organ in the body is out of tune it will affect the whole body. This can be explained by the principle called 'entrainment'⁴, made popular by the Dutch scientist Christian Huygens in the 17th century.

Recent scientific research has identified specific therapeutic application of the appropriate sound frequencies can help disorders in those parts of the body which they relate to. Through these principles it is possible to use sound to bring the body back into harmony, which is more like re-tuning a piano instead of having the need for drugs or surgery. An attempt for such sound healing will be done during the presentation of The Collection.

Sound creates colour

When one speaks of colour, actually coloured light is meant. Colour is simply light at a certain frequency, having a certain wavelength. Coloured light is that tiny visible part of the enormously huge electromagnetic spectrum⁵ that a human eye can perceive.

Sound and electromagnetism are also believed to be two totally different phenomena but also that, is a common misconception in the current knowledge. According to Reid (2006),

"[...]All electromagnetism in the Cosmos is a

Figure 6. The Cyma Glyph laser cut in organza fabric. A unique interfering pattern appears on the material when exposed to the beams of coloured LED's hidden in the clothing making it seem to come alive.

consequence of sound. Put differently, the two seemingly different types of energy are interconnected as electromagnetism would not exist without sound".

This means, that when the sound is created, atoms are condensed closer to each other or pushed further away as a result of the vibration. This movement of atoms is what gives birth to electromagnetism. Sound and electromagnetism (and thus colour) both are interconnected already from the moment of creation but are perceived with two different senses- seeing and hearing. The act of seeing sound is addressed in The Collection presentation, making a cross-connecting experience of the two seemingly different senses.

How does colour therapy work?

As mentioned before, colour is light energy. It is a high frequency energy in motion that affects us in different levels: physical, psychological and emotional. It is commonly known that colour is perceived by the eyes, but it can also be absorbed through the skin and even the skull. Also the electromagnetic field, also referred as the aura, absorbs light energy. Body can be given

- 4 When one vibrating object is exposed to other matter, it will influence the other matter to start vibrating at the same rate.
- 5 Electromagnetic radiation from small frequencies (radio waves) to exceedingly high values of ν (gamma rays). This spectrum includes visible light, X-rays and radio waves.

Figure 7. The human body and the placement of the seven main energy centers –chakras, with each their own location in/on the human body and the colour and sound frequencies that are ought to resonate with each one of them. In the collection, these interconnections are used for choosing the sound and coloured light, to fit the results of the GDV scan, in order to “charge” the chakras that lack energy.

colour energy by means of Solarized Water⁶, coloured silks, lamps with colour filters and by bringing people into specially coloured environments. These, amongst others, are a few examples of how colour therapy can be practiced. Also called Chromo therapy, it is a visual form of holistic healing⁷. Various types of colour therapy date back to ancient Egypt, Greece and China.

Human body energy centers

It is understood, that our wellbeing is not, of course, a physical issue only. That is to say, we are body, mind and spirit and none of these areas function entirely alone; each has an effect upon the other. A human body is believed to have seven main energy centers located along the spine, the so called *chakras* (Sanskrit word for “wheel of light”). The oldest written teachings about the Chakras come from the *Upanishads*⁸ dating around 7-800 B.C. in ancient India. The philosophy of *chakras* reappear incorporated in many Yoga and Tantric traditions and Chinese medicine principles.

Chakras are considered vortexes in which etheric energy⁹ can enter or leave the human energy body. In different spiritual teachings, it is believed that the state of chakras affect the physical, emotional, mental and spiritual aspects of the human body. Next to the spiritual approach, also according to the Dr. Richard Gerber’s book of “Vibrational Medicine” (2001), the etheric body (consisting of all energy centers together) is a subtle-energy template that guides the development of the physical body.

It is thus important to be aware of the health of the

energy body; make sure the *chakras* are healthy and aligned with each other. These energy vortexes, *chakras*, can be energized and brought back in harmony for instance by charging them with colour energy or sound vibration.

Each of the seven chakras is ought to resonate with one of the seven musical notes: C, D, E, F, G, A, B. Each of them has a unique vibrational frequency (Figure 7). Exposing the chakra to a certain sound frequency will

- 6 Water exposed to sunrays (energy) shining through a transparent coloured medium (colour filter, coloured glass). The water absorbs the vibrational energy of that particular colour. This water can be used for ingestion or bathing (parts of) the body.
- 7 The holistic concept in medical practice, which is distinct from the concept in the alternative medicine, upholds that all aspects of people’s needs including psychological, physical and social should be taken into account and seen as a whole.
- 8 A collection of texts of religious and philosophical nature, written in India probably between c. 800 BCE and c. 500 BCE, during a time when Indian society started to question the traditional Vedic religious order.
- 9 A type of very fine matter or substance. It permeates all physical matter and space throughout the universe. It is the same as that which is called chi, qi, vital force, prana and other names in various languages. The etheral energies of the human body, all together form the etheral body.

Figure 8. Test sample with a mini-microphone, micro-processor programmed to be able to analyze the tone spectrum and RGB LED's. The hardware is incorporated in the textile with special conductive thread. Later this circuit is incorporated in actual clothing design for the collection. The hardware is being hidden between layers of textile in a way, that only the beams of light are visible to the public.

cause the chakra to vibrate more in sync with the sound, according to the earlier described 'entrainment' principle. In this way, an "out of tune" chakra could be brought back to its healthy resonance, similar as a musical instrument. The lowest (root) chakra resonates with the lowest note (C) and respectively the highest (crown) chakra resonates with the highest note (B). In The Collection presentation, a piece of sound will be designed and directly played in accordance to the individual the *chakra*-status of the viewer.

The *chakras* are also each ought to resonate with one of the seven colours of the rainbow: red, orange, yellow, green, blue, indigo and violet. Each of the chakras is vibrating at a particular frequency and responds to a certain vibration or wavelength of light. This interconnection has a certain logic in as well. For instance, (the most dense) root chakra is said to resonate with the colour red, which is the colour with the longest wavelength, while the (least dense) crown chakra resonates with the colour violet, which respectively has the shortest wavelength. In The Collection presentation, a type of colour therapy will be practiced through the incorporated LED's in every outfit that are activated by the music that is being played in the room (Figure 8).

Light emitted by the human body

The human body literally glows, emitting a visible light in extremely small quantities at levels that vary for each person. These photons are 1 000 times less intense than the levels which can be seen with the naked eye. In fact, virtually all living creatures emit very weak light energy, without us noticing it.

This subtle energy can be captured with a special type of camera based on the Kirlian effect¹⁰. This technique is called Gas Discharge Visualization (GDV)¹¹.

A specialist in this field of science and medicine is a St. Petersburg based professor and physicist Dr. Korotkov¹². He has devoted his life for the development of this photography technique and has recently come to a model called "Bio Well" that is easy to use and is now available for the broader public. With this camera, each of the 10 fingertips are scanned and the emitted electrons and the photons are captured in photo and/or video (Figure 9). The images are then mapped to different organs and systems of the body, tapping into Chinese energy meridians. The software gives direct feedback about the *chakra*-balance and energy levels (Figure 10).

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- 10 Kirlian Effect is a visible electro-photonic glow of an object (see the picture on the right) in response to pulsed electrical field excitation.
 - 11 The appearance of images of the fluorescence (and, some argue, the biofield or aura) that surrounds living tissue after it has been exposed to a high-intensity field of electricity.
 - 12 Dr. Korotkov is a Professor of Physics at St. Petersburg Federal Research University of Informational Technologies, Mechanics and Optics in Saint Petersburg, Russia. He is a leading scientist internationally renowned for his pioneering research on the human energy field. Professor Korotkov developed the Gas Discharge Visualization technique, based on the Kirlian effect in 1995.

Figure 9. GDV (Gas Discharge Visualisation) technique capturing the photons and electrons coming from the human fingertips. This technique is based on the Kirlian effect and can be interpreted as a total-health indicator according to the Chinese meridian teachings. Before seeing the collection, the visitors will each have the chance to make their personal scan with the GDV device developed by Dr. Korotkov, PhD. The outcome of this scan, will influence the visitor's audiovisual experience of the collection.

Figure 10. A special software interprets the GDV scanned images. Particular places at the finger tops are representative of particular chakras, which in turn are believed to have direct connection to certain physical body parts/organs. The chakra-status results are then translated in the sound-design software which will determine the composition of the musical notes played at the collection presentation (the resonant notes of the "weakest" chakras will be the most prominent in the sound design).

Figure 11. A visualized mock-up of the final presentation of the collection. In a half-dark room, the seven outfits will be worn by models. The specially designed sound, fitting the visitor's chakra-status, will be playing through the speakers as the he enters the space. The sound will be picked up and recognized by the hardware and software in the outfits and will give impulses to the corresponding coloured lights in the clothing, together giving a sound & light therapy while the visitor is enjoying the show of the "Beings of Frequency".

The presentation

Each viewer would get the chance to scan his *chakra* status with the GDV Bio Well device, which would then be translated in sound design software and when played and activating the corresponding light emitting diodes incorporated in the clothing. In this way the viewer can enjoy the "Beings of Frequency" bringing him a special, individual light & sound show composed in a way to improve the physical and emotional state of the viewer (Figure 11).

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— *Special Sessions* —

Panel discussion: Cultural challenges of user research in Americas

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Topic Design practice and user research have a close and polemic relationship. It is known that user research may play the role of providing information that allows insights during the design process. On the other hand, professionals commonly report that structured data can limit creativity, or do not believe that the observation of everyday life can feed them novel and meaningful insights. This is common to observe, since the industry frequently uses design research to control risks, e.g. to maximize the chances of success of a product, rather than looking for creative insights. In America, researchers deal with many challenges to understand user experience. In addition to the known turbulent relationship between user research and design, many cultural issues also need to be addressed: users from distinct backgrounds express differently about their experiences due to cultural disparities that interfere in the way they express emotions; the market often tends to traditional uses of research, such as risk control; and many creative designers may feel oppressed when working with design guidelines that come from research. In this session, organizers report a series of experiences in Americas that facilitate the understanding of how to work with user research in this diverse continent.

Purpose This session explores how user research has been used by companies in Latin and North America, as well as the challenges encountered in dealing with diverse cultural backgrounds. It provides attendants the opportunity to understand the gap between how this discipline could contribute to design practices and how it is actually being incorporated in everyday practice of organizations, including how to address user diversity in these projects. The main purpose of this special session is to allow a critical view on the topic, reducing the bridge between academia and industry, based on actual and current market experiences.

Keywords *User research in Americas, Design research, Design practice, Relationship between user research and design, Cultural issues in design research*

Panel discussion: Can design contribute to subjective well-being and happiness? Multidisciplinary insights and experiences

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Topic This panel session focuses on subjective well-being / happiness and the contribution that design can have herein.

‘Happiness’ and ‘well-being’ are one of the major, if not the ultimate, life goal. Studying happiness is important, relevant and timely because firstly, there seems to be a societal need to focus on this topic. Secondly, it is highly relevant from an economic perspective, as happy people seem to be successful in many domains of life, whereby these successes are at least in part due to their happiness (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005). Thirdly, happiness has also become an issue on the political agenda.

The last decades, researchers from diverse disciplines have tried to point to the essence of well-being and happiness. In addition, the last few years, different researchers from various design disciplines begun to investigate whether their discipline can contribute to happiness, and, if so, how this contribution can look like. However, to date, there is no consensus on the conceptualization of well-being and happiness (Lyubomirsky, 2007 ; Sheldon & Lyubomirsky, 2007 ; Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). All design research with a focus on well-being and happiness that is currently being performed, thus can be considered to be pioneering work.

Purpose

Aim:

- (i) Develop an understanding of approaches employed in different design disciplines regarding design for well-being and happiness
- (ii) Discuss and disseminate insights and experiences
- (iii) Support further growth of field of knowledge

Relevance for the D&E conference:

- (i) Bring together a multidisciplinary team of experts regarding design for well-being and happiness
- (ii) Dissemination of knowledge regarding the question how design can contribute to happiness

Relevance for the community:

- (i) Help this field of knowledge to further evolve: dissemination of knowledge can enhance future research and collaboration initiatives
- (ii) In the long run: make more people happy through design

Keywords *Subjective well-being and happiness, Assessment, Enabling activities, Multidisciplinary reflections and insights*

Workshop: Design ideation through humour

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Topic Brainstorming is one of the most common design creativity methods, yet it has been criticized for failing to change perspectives of the design problem (McFadzean, 1998). Also, although brainstorming rules prohibit judgement and criticism whilst encouraging 'wild ideas', the rules are often neglected in practice (Matthews, 2009).

Humour has long been associated with creativity. Studies have found that comedians, and those who perform well in 'sense of humour' testing are highly creative individuals with a skill for finding surprising connections between seemingly unrelated ideas (Kudrowitz and Wallace, 2010; Humke and Schaefer, 1996). A humorous atmosphere can also improve creativity and problem-solving by reducing inhibitions and enhancing freedom of expression (Ziv, 1976; Isen et al., 1987). There are also analogies to be made between the processes of creating humour and engineering design. These findings present an opportunity to reinvigorate the early phase of the design process, when divergent, creative thinking is most valued.

This EPSRC and AHRC funded research explores the link between humour and design creativity through the development of new ideation methods that integrate the structure and principles of humour creation processes (such as comedy improvisation) into ideation processes to solve complex engineering problems from new and surprising perspectives.

Purpose Our research explores the influence of both the thought patterns associated with humour creation and the positive emotions associated with humour appreciation on creativity at the early stages of engineering design.

This session invites the D&E community to participate in a design ideation inspired by the principles and processes of improvised comedy, gaining insight into its effects on mood, group dynamics and outcomes. It is also an opportunity to discuss the significance of emotion during the design process in creating products that are both surprising and satisfying.

Keywords *Humour, Creativity, Ideation, Design engineering, Improvisation*

Workshop / exhibition: HOSPITAbLe - 'Thinking with things', exploring the domestication of healthcare

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Topic The hospital is the traditional and familiar controlled domain where healthcare is defined and delivered. However the consequences of an older society, escalating costs of healthcare services and a shortage of personnel and facilities have put pressure on the healthcare system to deliver more support and treatments on an outpatient basis and in peoples home. The home and the hospital bring together very different cultural practices and environments and this inexorable geographical shift in care has potential impact on our physical and emotional relationship with our home space. Objects and artefacts offer valuable ways to begin to understand the richness and complexity in people's lives. The authors draw on the value of 'thinking with things' as a method and central to this is the notion of exhibition as a research tool that becomes a meeting space that enables this to happen. Exhibition provides a theatre for conversation and becomes the medium and method for data collection and creates the conduit, through which societal assumptions relating to ageing and healthcare care can be made visible, explored and challenged.

This special session will engage participants with objects and artefacts' as a method to build understanding of the factors users identify as being important.

Purpose Future delivery of healthcare is one of societies biggest challenges. We will briefly explore how future healthcare at home might challenge the symbolic meaning and relationship within our home. The session will explores the role of critical artefacts and their use as physical metaphors to prompt discussion that might help inform our understanding and emotional relationship with this new hybrid ambiguous landscape.

The artefacts present a hybrid ambiguous landscape each positioning metaphorical questions within the context of our future healthcare. "The question is not, 'What is the answer?' The question is 'What is the question?' (Licklider 1960).

Keywords *Design, Healthcare, Critical artefacts, Aesthetics, Exhibition as research*

Workshop: Positive Design. Designing the road of happiness

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Topic *“If you want to increase your happiness, don’t buy new products, change your behaviour.”* Positive psychologists sometimes advise that not too much ought to be expected from the contributions to subjective well-being made by consumer products (Nicolao, Irwin, & Goodman, 2009). The ‘Positive Design’ workshop challenges this view by proposing that design can increase happiness. The central question addressed is: How can design contribute to human flourishing? Positive Design is an umbrella term for all forms of design, design research and design intention in which explicit attention is paid to the effects of design on the subjective well-being of individuals and communities (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013; Pohlmeier & Desmet, 2014). In their workshop, Anna and Pieter will introduce their view on Positive Design and present examples of how design can help people in finding balance between pleasure, purpose in life, and virtuous behaviour. They will introduce some of the key research questions in the domain of Positive Design and detail a Positive Design Framework in-depth. In addition to providing relevant background knowledge, a number of hands-on exercises will be conducted to familiarize participants with essential concepts and design methods. The aim of the workshop is to inform, engage, and inspire; offering a balance between theory & research on the one hand, and experiences & design examples on the other.

Keywords *Design for human values, Design for well-being, Theoretical foundations of design and emotion*

Workshop: Putting design at the heart: Weaving empathy into service design methods

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Topic Designers strive to create things that make an impact on people by viewing their work through a human-centered lens. Whether it's speaking to the people who will be using a service or product, or shadowing those who will be at the heart of a new process, an emotional understanding of human needs is both fundamental and transformational in design work. Human-centered design is empathetic by definition, as it places people at the center of the creative process. However once the process starts, designers don't often get to address how empathy is reflected in their methods and design artifacts.

Designers can go beyond approaching their work with design empathy alone – they have to work within the constituency that they are designing for. This workshop will touch on approaching design work with “deep empathy” and how weaving this type of approach into design methods and artifacts is a powerful way to capture emotion and ensure that design empathy endures.

Purpose As designers, we strive to embody empathetic design. But too often, our design methods fail to make the most of the time we spend with the people for whom we're designing or working. The Design and Emotion conference is an ideal setting to invite designers to contemplate the level of design empathy that informs their work from start to finish.

The purpose of this session is to inspire designers to weave “deep empathy” and emotion into their design methods. We'll explain how this led to success, using our work within the social services space as an example. The workshop will equip participants with an understanding of how a careful choice of design methods will help them design with empathy and make a lasting impact.

Keywords *Journey mapping, Service blueprinting, Social services, Living labs, Co-design, Design empathy, Design methods*

Workshop: Rethinking the profession and education of retail design

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Topic We strongly believe retail design is becoming a discipline in its own right. Today, the growth of digital technology asks for new ways of retailing. The intertwining of retail and society makes it challenging for retailers to stay relevant in relation to the consumers changing habits. Fitch believed that 'shopping is the purpose of life' (Fitch, 2012). His belief shifted the way all stakeholders in retail thought about what retail and retail design should be about. By recognising that retail design is more than just designing a store's interior, Fitch set the tone in creating a discipline that crossed over various disciplines, and incorporated retail design and architecture, alongside product and packaging design. Today, the discipline is changing again under the pressure of the digital evolution and changing consumer (Christiaans & Almendra, 2012). Retailers today should extend their business with an omni-channel approach. Retailers are in urge to create seamless brand experiences which transcend the boundaries of online and offline channels (Quartier, 2016). This has repercussions for the field of retail design and the role of the designer in the design process. This short work-shop wants to contribute in rethinking the discipline's and profession of retail design. Therefore, want to bring designers together to think about a holistic interdisciplinary design approach embracing all retailer's channels.

Purpose The retail business has evolved into the design of a customer holistic experience for which specialists from diverse disciplines need to work together (Teufel & Zimmerman, 2015). This merge generates an opportunity to create physical and digital spaces that are consistent, coherent and above all, complementary. However, for this domain to really grow and flourish, the existing gaps between different design disciplines need to disappear. We want to open this discussion (in te hope to find a way to close the gap) to hear what other designers from other disciplines think about what the profession of retail design should be in the near future. The D&E conference offers a great opportunity to bring de-signers, interested in the topic of retail design, together.

Keywords *Retail design, Retail design education, Inter-disciplinal, Research in retail design, Retail 3.0*

Workshop: Technology-supported emotion measurement

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Topic Emotion measurement is a vital aspect for new product development and product improvements (see e.g. Desmet & Schifferstein, 2012). New technological devices, data mining, and social media offer many opportunities to invigorate design research. The focus of this small workshop is the question, how new technologies can be utilized for design research and emotion measurement in particular. The range of applicable technologies spans from eye-tracking, to EEG measuring, to semi-automated facial expression recognition in photographs based on data mining technologies or crowdsourcing, etc. Furthermore, many traditional technologies for emotion tracking are becoming smaller and mobile, which allows also in-field research (e.g. EEG scanners). Triangulating different data sources might result in new insights and improve user research significantly. For example, measuring people's emotions in relation to their location (e.g. tracked through GPS or indoor positioning tools) might indicate the influence of the environment on that person's wellbeing. In this small workshop we want to present an overview of available technologies, outline our own experiences with several technology-supported research projects, demonstrate some selected tools, and develop ideas for new research approaches together with the workshop participants.

Purpose The goal of this small workshop is threefold: 1) We want to give the workshop participants an overview of technologies currently available on the market as well as upcoming trends. Some selected tools for measuring emotions will be provided for hands-on experimentation. 2) The workshop will be used to build a network of researchers interested in the topic. And 3) it provides a platform for jointly developing ideas for new research approaches based on new technologies. As a result, participants will gain new insights and ideas for their own research on users' emotions.

Keywords *Research methodologies and methods, New technologies, Emotion measurement, Science theory, User research*

Workshop: Designing for Happiness: A workshop about symbolic meaning

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Topic Research on happiness argues that material possessions have a limited impact on happiness [1, 2], and that engaging in certain activities is a more effective approach [3, 4]. Accordingly, experience-enabling products have been deemed useful for increasing happiness [5, 6, 7]. We propose that, in addition to experience-enabling products, certain material possessions that hold significant narratives can similarly be a valid way to support happiness. In that sense, the symbolic meaning of products can have a role in designing for happiness. Symbolically meaningful possessions allow the re-consumption of experiences (souvenirs) [8], represent relationships [9], help communicate one's identity [10], and provide an anchor for meaningful narratives (heirlooms) [11]. Designing with symbolic meaning represents an opportunity for design because it can potentially increase the relevance of products, result in higher quality interactions and encourage subjective well-being. Previous research [12] identified six happiness-related symbolic meanings in products, based on Ryff's model of psychological well-being [13]: positive relations with others, personal growth, purpose in life, environmental mastery, autonomy, and self-acceptance. The six meanings were used to develop 16 design directions to inspire designers to create products that are predisposed for symbolic meaning attribution, and therefore can have an impact on users' happiness [14].

Purpose Happiness is a universally desirable human goal. Drawing from research on Positive Psychology, Positive Design focuses on individual well-being and on the opportunities for design to contribute to an improvement towards positive states of feeling and being. The workshop aims to communicate research on Positive Design (design for happiness) and to disseminate a tool that can help designers create products that are predisposed for symbolic meaning attribution. This approach is expected to generate an improved interaction with products, which can result longer user-product relations and generate a positive impact in the happiness of users.

Keywords *Symbolic meaning, Positive design, Happiness, Design tool, Design workshop*

Workshop: Reframing Crash Course: How to design meaningful citizenship?

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Topic The rise of active citizenship marks the transition from a welfare society to a participation society. So-called third generation citizens' participation indicates that the relation between government and society has flipped: the civil society initiates, the government participates (Lenos, Sturm & Vis, 2006). However, third generation participation appears to be problematic in its execution. Various questions arise, for instance: How to engage all citizens, is this possible and/or desirable?

Although Social Economic Status (SES) explains participation to a large extent (Verba et al., 1995), in general it is self-confidence to play a key role: "The *self-confident* citizen is likely to be the *active* citizen" (Almond & Verba, 1963/1989). In other words: engagement requires self-confidence. Hence, the Reframing Crash Course will take self-confidence as a starting point to design meaningful citizenship in the future.

By using the renowned *reframing process**, the Crash Course inspires participants to let go of the 'here and now' and to apply the tools provided to anticipate the future of citizenship. Reframing is firmly rooted in a consciously constructed – future – world. It goes through specific steps and several phases that provide a clear design trajectory for each project. Since the process defines the goal and not the means, the method can be applied to broader, multi-stakeholder and societal topics such as citizens' participation.

* The reframing process is based on the Vision in Product design (ViP) method, which has been developed at the Delft University of Technology by Prof. Ir. Matthijs van Dijk and Prof. dr. Paul Hekkert.

Purpose

The aim of the Crash Course is to:

1. Experience the reframing process;
2. Explore the future context of citizenship;
3. Enjoy collaborating in a cross-disciplinary context.

As reframing focuses on value patterns and design relations rather than products, its process is particularly fit for the purpose of analyzing human behavior and societal relations.

Keywords *Citizenship, Design thinking, Engagement, Reframing, Self-confidence*

Workshop: Laban Movement Analysis in design research: An embodied experience

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Topic Laban Movement Analysis (LMA) is a movement notation system widely used among dancers and choreographers, actors, body-oriented psychotherapists, and more recently in user-experience design. Like music, movement can be observed and notated. The experience of the mover and those observing is a relationship with the environment that can be recorded on a deeper level than reported feedback, an embodied experience (Bartenieff & Lewis, 1980). What is a user or user group's body language? How can designers use this information to better develop spaces that facilitate user needs? This special session workshop proposes using LMA as a tool to observe and record movement in order to analyze the meaning of an experience within a space or with a product.

Purpose The proposed session ties the topics of *ambiguity*, in the uncomfortable interactions often experienced in the pursuit of understanding human behavior, of *poetry*, enhancing the ability to tell a user's story, of *empathy* and *spirituality*, in co-designing by embodying and witnessing the present experience of the user, and overall in informing the study of how the built environment, micro and macro, influence human *well-being*. In celebration of D&E, the session proposes the cross-disciplinary use, from psychology to the performing arts to design, of a movement observation tool applicable to further explorations of human emotions and connections.

Keywords *Laban movement analysis, Movement behavior, Body language, Embodied experience, Ethnography*

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